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CHALLENGES OF FEDERALISM IN INDIA

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Abstract

This study delves into the complexities of India's federalism, analyzing both the practical challenges faced in its implementation and the legal framework that underpins it. The Indian Constitution seeks to create a balance of power and responsibility between the central and state governments, blending features of both unitary and federal systems. The research examines key constitutional provisions and amendments that define the structure of the federal government, including the division of legislative authority, fiscal relations, and administrative processes. Despite the constitutional design aimed at maintaining this balance, effective federalism in India faces significant obstacles. Administrative inefficiencies, political tensions, and economic disparities often lead to strained center-state relations. This study explores these challenges, shedding light on instances of both conflict and cooperation between various levels of government. It seeks to trace the evolution of Indian federalism through a critical analysis of case laws, policy decisions, and intergovernmental dialogues.

Additionally, the paper investigates the impact of regionalism, coalition politics, and economic liberalization on India's federal structure. The study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the practical aspects of constitutional federalism and suggests necessary reforms to improve its effectiveness. The findings highlight the importance of ongoing dialogue and adaptation to ensure that India's federal system remains resilient and responsive to the diverse needs of its population.

Keywords: Federalism, Indian Constitution, Center-State Relations, Legislative Powers, Administrative Federalism, Financial Relations, Regionalism, Coalition Politics

Challenges of Federalism in India

1. Political Dynamics

India's political system often leads to conflicts between the central and state governments. These tensions arise from differing political ideologies and goals, particularly when different political parties govern at the federal and state levels. Such disparities can influence policy implementation and governance, making it difficult to maintain a unified approach to administration.

- **Party Politics:** When the ruling party in a state differs from the party in power at the center, cooperation becomes challenging. Disagreements over policy implementation, resource allocation, and government priorities are common, potentially hindering effective governance.
- **Governor's Role:** The governor, appointed by the central government, is meant to oversee state affairs. However, in some instances, the governor's actions may be perceived as overreaching or divisive, particularly when the state government is at odds with the central administration. This becomes especially contentious when the governor invokes the powers granted under Article 356 (President's Rule), which can be seen as an imposition of central authority over the state.

2. Economic Disparities

Economic disparities between states pose significant challenges to India's federal system. Wealthier states, with greater resources, experience higher living standards and more advanced development,

while poorer states struggle to catch up. This imbalance creates tensions and hampers equitable growth across the country.

- **Resource Allocation:** The distribution of central funding often becomes contentious, as states compete for a larger share of resources. Perceptions of favoritism or neglect can arise when certain states feel they are being sidelined, exacerbating regional inequalities and fueling discontent.
- **Special Category States:** Some states receive additional financial support from the central government due to their unique needs or challenges. While this is intended to address regional disparities, it can lead to resentment in other states that feel disadvantaged or overlooked, further complicating intergovernmental relations.

3. Administrative Inefficiencies

India's bureaucratic structure often leads to administrative inefficiencies that hinder effective governance and policy implementation.

- **Coordination Problems:** Lack of coordination among the various levels of government can result in delays and inefficiencies. This issue is particularly evident in the implementation of centrally sponsored programs, where state governments may have different priorities, complicating the execution of national initiatives.
- **Corruption and Red Tape:** Bureaucratic red tape and corruption further exacerbate governance challenges. These issues can lead to the misallocation of resources, slow down decision-making processes, and undermine public trust in government institutions, making it difficult to achieve efficient and transparent administration.

4. Regionalism

Regionalism, fueled by linguistic, cultural, and ethnic diversity, can lead to calls for greater autonomy and, in some cases, secessionist movements.

- **State Reorganization:** There has been a persistent demand for the creation of new states based on linguistic or ethnic considerations. While some reorganizations have been relatively peaceful, others have resulted in significant political and social instability, highlighting the challenges of accommodating regional aspirations within the federal structure.
- **Secessionist Movements:** Several regions, including Jammu & Kashmir and parts of the Northeast, have witnessed secessionist movements that pose a direct threat to the integrity of the federal system. These movements challenge the very foundations of India's unity, complicating the relationship between the center and the states.

5. Coalition Politics

The widespread presence of coalition governments at both the central and state levels has notable implications for India's federal structure.

- **Policy Paralysis:** Coalition governments often face challenges of policy stagnation due to the need for extended negotiations and compromises among various political parties. This can be particularly problematic when it comes to implementing policies that require broad consensus, leading to delays or lack of decisive action.
- **Influence of Regional Parties:** In coalition governments, regional parties often play a key role, exerting considerable influence over national policies to reflect regional concerns. While this can lead to more inclusive governance by addressing local priorities, it can also result in

conflicts of interest, as regional demands may not always align with the broader national agenda.

6. Economic Liberalization

The economic reforms of 1991 transformed India's economy but also introduced new challenges for the country's federal structure.

- **Competition Among States:** Economic liberalization has led to increased competition among states as they strive to attract investment. While this has spurred development in some areas, it has also widened the gap between states that can successfully attract investment and those that struggle to do so, exacerbating regional inequalities.
- **Fiscal Federalism:** The introduction of the Goods and Services Tax (GST) is a key example of how economic reforms have impacted federalism. By consolidating various state taxes into a single national tax, the GST has raised concerns about the financial autonomy of states. While the GST Council is working to address these issues, disagreements over tax rates and revenue-sharing continue to pose challenges to fiscal federalism.

7. Governance and Policy Implementation

Effective governance and policy implementation are essential for the success of the federal structure, but several challenges hinder this process.

- **Centrally Sponsored Schemes:** The implementation of centrally sponsored schemes often faces difficulties at the state level due to differences in administrative capacity and varying state priorities. These disparities can lead to inconsistent outcomes and inefficiencies, undermining the effectiveness of national programs.
- **Judicial Intervention:** The judiciary often plays a crucial role in resolving conflicts between the central government and the states. However, when judicial decisions are seen as encroaching on the autonomy of state governments, it can lead to tensions and debates about the balance of power between the center and the states.

8. Center-State Conflicts in India

Conflicts between the center and states in India stem from various issues, including disputes over jurisdiction, resource allocation, and policy implementation.

- **Water Disputes:** Interstate water conflicts, such as those involving the Cauvery and Krishna rivers, frequently require federal intervention. These disputes highlight the complexities of managing shared resources within a federal framework and underline the need for equitable and sustainable solutions.
- **Law and Order:** The central government's mandate to ensure law and order, particularly in cases of terrorism or internal unrest, can sometimes clash with state governments, which may perceive such interventions as encroachments on their autonomy.

Conclusion

India's federal challenges arise from a mix of social, administrative, political, and economic factors. Addressing these requires continuous efforts toward communication, collaboration, and adaptability. A successful federal system in India hinges on maintaining effective governance, ensuring fair resource distribution, and respecting the autonomy of state governments. This adaptability is essential for preserving India's unity and integrity while meeting the diverse needs of its people.

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PARTICIPATION OF WOMEN IN POLITICS: A STUDY OF KARNATAKA**Sangeeta Chandrasha Dandoti &¹Prof. Chandrakant M. Yatanoor²**¹Research Scholar, Dept. of Political Science, Gulbarga University, Kalaburagi, Karnataka.²Professor and Chairman, Dept. of Political Science, Gulbarga University, Kalaburagi, Karnataka.

Abstract

The representation of women in Indian politics, the difficulties they encounter and the results of their participation are the main topics of this analytical study. Examining the historical context, it highlights significant individuals and turning points in the political empowerment of women. The study investigates the status of women's representation in Indian politics today and pinpoints the causes of their under-representation. At the grassroots level, it talks about the reservation policy and how it affects women's involvement. Examining only electoral forms of participation, limits explanation of how, when and why men and women participate in the political process. We discuss how communitarian and private space are grounds for political participation. We call for considering a wider set of contextual factors to explain variation across place, time and modes of participation in politics. Further, cross-level links between the international, national and local can help theorize how context creates opportunities and incentives for particular forms of participation. Specifically, taking into account the contours of women's participation and women's organizations may improve understanding of gender differences and identity in political participation in Karnataka. The low political representation of women has been noted to create some challenges, which this article has assessed. Women's participation in parliament has been interpreted in order to minimize or enhance obstacles and to examine women's political empowerment; ultimately, recommendations have been made in this study.

Keywords: Women in Politics, Women Empowerment, Participation, Organization, Indian Politics, Gender Differences, Understanding and Representation.

I – INTRODUCTION:

A topic of great importance and research is the role of women in politics, particularly in India, a nation renowned for its diverse culture, democratic governance, and rich culture tapestry. The complex factors underlying women's political participation in India are examined in this analytical study. It aims to illuminate the obstacles, possibilities, and changing patterns that have influenced the political representation of women in India. The largest democracy in the world, Indian, has a lengthy and intricate history of gender inequality that has shown itself in many areas of life, including politics. Even though the country's constitution is progressive and inclusive, men have always held a dominant position in politics. Much progress has been achieved in removing these obstacles and promoting more gender equality in politics throughout the years.¹

Women's status in India has fluctuated greatly since ancient times, ranging from equal status in the ancient period to wearing veils in the medieval period. Women's rights regained power in post-independence India and have been steadily improving since then. Women in post-independence India have been involved in practically every aspect of economic activity. Including day-to-day domestic tasks, voting for better government, and active politics. India had elected a woman Prime Minister, Indira Gandhi, and a woman President, Pratibha Patil. India has a substantial representation of women in micro level politics, which was attained by reserving seats for women.²

Political representation is the activity of making citizens present in public policy making processes. Since ancient times, representations of women have been abysmally low with a few exceptions of Razia Sultan, Rani Laxmi Bai, and Sarojini Naidu etc. Political representation is the hallmark of democratic setup. Democracy implies equality of all humans, men and women. As against this women are excluded from different walks of life more visibly in politics. Despite the Preamble

providing for equality as one of the objectives and inclusion of Fundamental Rights, Directive Principles of state politics, Article 324, Article 325, Article 326, the representation of women in electoral politics is not up to the mark.³

According to the latest Inter-Parliamentary Union's (IPU) report, "Women in Parliament in 2021", tells us that the women Parliamentarians across the globe stand at 26.4%. And the 17th Lok Sabh of India had known for the highest women power in the history of independent India but to its tall claim, only 14% of the present Lok Sabha is women (78/543). Thus, the United Nation's body for women, i.e. 'UN Women' says, "at the current rate, gender equality in the highest positions of power will not be reached for another 130 years".⁴ In 2023, progress on women's representation in parliament was slow and mixed. Globally, the share of women MPs stood at 26.9% On January 2024- only 0.4% points higher than it was 12 months earlier. This represented a similar rate of progress as in 2022, but slower than in the preceding years.⁵ Women's Political Participation is a necessary prerequisite for gender equality and true democracy. It encourages women's direct participation in public decision- making and serves as a means of ensuring more accountability to women.⁶ Considerations of women's political agency have become more integrated in studies of Indian electoral politics.

II – TYPES OF POLITICAL PARTICIPATION:

Political Participation denotes a series of political activities of the individuals. It included the activities like voting, campaigning, discussing politics, attending political meetings, convincing another person to vote in a particular way, distributing party literature, contributing money to campaigns and contacting officials and other activities of this nature. He brings these activities under the following three categories: "(1) Gladiatorial; (2) Transitional and (3) Spectatorial." Viewing the later developments he has broadened his outlook on the concept of political participation.⁷

III – WOMEN AND POLITICS:

Indian women in politics, isn't a new phenomena that could only have been seen after 1947. Well, from antiquity, though an Indian woman was subjected to constant subjugation under the unquestionable authority of the Smrithis and the Shastras, but she always has been an essential part of a council of wise men and such status was granted to her under the role of a mother, wife or daughter and even at times as a renowned scholar. Gargi Vachaknavi, the only women philosopher in the King Janaka's court of Mithila is quite famously known for her questioning of Yajnyavalkya on Brahmacharaym, Marriage and Love, as bondage and natural elements, and even Maitrei, the 2nd wife of Yajnavalkya was the addressee of his popular discourse on immortality and death.

Through the likes of Akkamahadevi (in the court of Anubhava Manttapa), Razia Begum Sultana, Chand Bibi (Bahamanis and guardian of Adil Shah and proponent of “Deccan reign”), Rani Lakshmbai, Rani Abbakka, Kittur Rani Chennamma, Gayatri Devi (princess of Cooch Behar , Rajmata of Jaipur and a MP), Viajalaksmhi Pandit, Sucitra Kripalani (CM), Sarojini Naidu, and so on so forth, it becomes evidently clear that throughout medieval and modern India, the women weren’t new to the quarters of scholarship, power and polity.

Now, in modern state of erstwhile Mysore, women too had their fair share of contribution to the politics. Umabai Kundapur is known for touring all over the state in-order to bring women volunteers for the annual session of National Congress, and then Bellary Siddamma for her participation in Shivpur Congress Session in 1938 and they are followed by Jagadevitai Ligade and Krishnabai from Honnavara rendered their notable services to the Swadeshi Movement. So, then why is that today, the women are under-represented in the Politics? This could be attributed to various factors ranging from locality, sex ratio, party politics and largely the general perception of Indian men.⁸

There was little international or coordinated attempt to build inclusive electoral spaces for women after independence. Women’s seats in the legislature were not reserved under the 1950 Constitution. Following independence, women’s political participation was generally limited by social conventions that shaped opportunities and views of women’s involvement in politics. These perceptions were sometimes specific to men and sometimes shared by women.⁹

Overall, women’s participation in politics throughout the freedom movement appeared to wane following independence. Women’s involvement in politics and political competition became limited to familial connections rather than being motivated by curiosity and cultural encouragement to participate actively. Political parties, following the dominant cultural attitude, ignored this issue and systematically excluded women from electoral participation.¹⁰

Political Parties, on the other hand, allocated a few seats in the general elections to women as recognition of their commitment to the war for Indian independence. This is obvious in the inaugural Lok Sabha elections in 1952, where women could win and occupy only 4.4% of the total seats in the Lower House of Parliament. (Table 3.1).

Table 3.1. Representation of Women in Lok Sabha 1952 – 2024.

Lok Sabha	Total No. of Seats	No. of Women Members.	% of Total.
First (1952)	489	22	22
Second(1957)	494	27	5.4
Third(1962)	494	34	6.7
Fourth(1967)	523	31	5.9
Fifth(1971)	521	22	4.2
Sixth(1977)	544	19	3.4
Seventh(1980)	544	28	5.1
Eighth(1984)	544	44	8.1
Ninth(1989)	529	28	5.3
Tenth(1991)	509	36	7.0
Eleventh(1996)	541	40	7.4
Twelfth(1998)	545	44	8.0
Thirteenth(1999)	543	48	8.8
Fourteenth(2004)	543	45	8.1
Fifteenth(2009)	543	59	10.9
Sixteenth(2014)	543	61	11.2
Seventeenth(2019)	543	78	14.4
Eighteenth(2024)	543	74	13.6

Source: Election Commission of India, New Delhi.

Note: *Including one nominated member.

Despite constitutional provisions ensuring gender equality, the call for greater representation of women in political institutions in India was taken up seriously until after the report of the committee on the status of Women in India.¹¹ This stated that women's presence in political institutions, particularly at the grassroots level, should be strengthened by a policy of seats reservations for women. As a result, the National Perspective Plan for Women advocated for a 30% quota for women at all levels of elective bodies.¹²

Women's organizations and gender activists, on the other hand, argued that reservation should be limited to the panchayat level in order to stimulate grassroots participation of women in electoral politics. The national consensus around this demand led in the ratification of the 73rd and 74th Amendments to the Indian Constitution in 1993, which established 33% reservation for women in local government organizations. This has been done "in all the states of India without evoking any hostility or opposition from male politicians or the general public." In 1995, the issue of affirmative action for women arose again, this time with an emphasis on reservations for women in Parliament. Initially, most political parties agreed on this requirement in principle, but disagreements quickly emerged. When the Bill addressing this subject was introduced in the Eleventh Parliament in 1997, numerous political parties and groups expressed concerns about elitism and overlapping quotas for women in general, as well as for lower caste women.¹³ The proposed Bill, which was introduced in Parliament 20 years ago, is still accumulating dust, and there are no clear indicators when it will be implemented.

IV - PARTICIPATION OF WOMEN IN POLITICS:

1. The Status of Political Representation of Women In India:

2. Participation of Women in Karnataka Politics:

1. The Status of Political Representation of Women in India:

A - Representation of Women in Parliament over the years:

- Women made up just 4.41% of the strength of the Lower House in 1952. The number increased to more than 6% in the Lok Sabha held a decade later.
- However, the number dipped to below 4% in 1971, ironically, with Indira Gandhi, India's first and only woman Prime Minister, at the helm.
- There has been a slow, but steady rise in women's representation (with a few exceptions). The women representation crossed the 10% mark in 2009 and peaked at 14.36% in 2019.
- Of the 74 women MPs elected in 2024, 43 are first time MPs. Women MPs have an average age of 50 years and are younger as compared to the overall age of the House, which is 56 years. These women MPs are as educated as their male counterparts, with 78% completing under graduation.¹⁴

B – State Legislative assembly representation:

The representation of women in State Legislative Assemblies has been low. The highest is in Chhattisgarh (14.44%), West Bengal (13.70%), Jharkhand (12.35%), Rajasthan (12.00%), Uttar Pradesh (11.66%), Uttarakhand (11.43%), NCT of Delhi (11.43%), Punjab (11.11%), Bihar (10.70%), Haryana (10.00%), Sikkim (9.38%), Madhya Pradesh (9.13%), Maharashtra (8.33%), Manipur (8.33%), Odisha (8.90%), Andhra Pradesh (8.00%), Kerala (7.86%), Goa (7.50%), Gujarat (7.14%), Himachal Pradesh (5.88), Tamil Nadu (5.13%), Telangana (5.04%), Tripura (5.00%), Arunachal Pradesh (5.00%), Meghalaya (5.08%), Assam (4.76%), Karnataka (3.14%), Puducherry (3.33%), Jammu and Kashmir (2.30%), Mizoram (0%), and Nagaland (0%).¹⁵

C – Comparison with Global Standards:

According to the Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU) 'Women in Parliament' Report (2021), the global percentage of women in parliament was 26.1%. India ranks lower than 140 other nations in terms of the number of women serving in their national legislatures. Even though the representation of women in Lok Sabha has increased in post independence (~16% in 17th Lok Sabha), India is behind a number of countries of Africa and South Asia (like Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka).¹⁶

The last 20 years in women's political participation and representation in India, discusses India's stalled progress in improvements to women's descriptive representation, despite progress in local government since the 1990s. Recent milestones in women's political leadership are discussed, including first appointments and elections to constitutional offices and senior women political leaders' party leadership. However, notable exceptions aside, senior women leaders' presence has declined recently since the passing of a generation. On substantive representation of 'women's interests', governments and political parties continue to invoke women's diverse, intersectional

political subjectivities as voters, citizens, clients, community members, workers and with recognition of women's increasingly mobilized voting power. Never the fewer women, especially among marginalized communities, are regularly still denied full agency, justice, rights, entitlements and experience continued, new and re-worked forms of violence, including in electoral politics.¹⁷

2. Participation of Women in Karnataka Politics:

Women's participation is a milestone in the history of the South Indian state of Karnataka. It was way back in 1930 that, for the first time in the history of the old Mysore state, Smt. Sakamma and Smt. Kamamma Dasappa, two women, entered the Mysore Representative Assembly. The next year, a significant first step was taken to amend the Hindu law regarding the rights of women and the widow's ability to adopt children, all progressive steps towards expanding the gambit of rights for women. Karnataka had its first woman speaker in its Legislative Assembly in K.S.Nagarathamma from 1972-78, a lady who was elected from Gundlupet Constituency, with only a single break in 1978.

Karnataka is a state where some amazing women have held leadership positions. Leeladevi R Prasad applauded the then Chief Minister of Karnataka, Shri Ramakrishna Hegde for addressing this situation and bringing about reservation for women in the State local bodies and also in the cooperative movement. (2003:16) Mr. Ramakrishna Hegde, considered a champion of democratic decentralisation, passed the Karnataka Zilla Panchayat, Taluk Panchayat, Mandal Panchayat and Nyaya Panchayat Act in 1983, reduced the age of voting to these elective bodies to 18 and reserved thirty per cent of seats in these bodies for women. Many opine that if not for 50% reservation at the local level that was introduced by Ramakrishna Hegde in the state way back in the early 1980s, the state would not have seen such representation of women that it does today. In fact, this Karnataka model of reservation for women was later adopted by others, including the late Prime Minister Shri Rajiv Gandhi in the 64th Amendment to the Constitution of India.

1962 remains the only year when 18 women legislators won seats into the Karnataka State Assembly. In 1967, K. S. Nagarathamma became the first female candidate to become an MLA in Karnataka after defeating K. B. Jayadevappa. But post 1963, this number has declined steadily and has been in single digits, except in 1989, when 10 women MLAs were elected. Karnataka's 14th Legislative Assembly had less than 3% women with only six elected women and one nominated in its entire strength of 225. There were a total of 175 female candidates of the 2945 candidates. The Congress gave tickets to 8; the BJP had 7 contestants and JD(S) scored high among the parties with 12 candidates in the fray. Sixty-seven of the women were independents.¹⁸ And Lok Sabha Elections of Karnataka we can see three seats of women's and this is the best Representation of Women in the Parlimentaent for the second time after 1991 Lok Sabha elections, this is also the election in which women voters outvoted men in 17 of the 28 Lok Sabha constituencies held in 2023- 2024. Of the six candidates, Congress fielded Dr. Prabha Mallikarjun and Priyanka Jarkiholi have won from Davanagere and Chikkodi constituencies respectively. Both are political greenhorns and belong to political families. Priyanka is the Daughter of Minister of Public Works Department Sathish Jarkiholi and Prabha is the wife of Mines and Geology Minister S Mallikarjun. BJP's Shobha Karandlaje has emerged victorious from Bangalore north, becoming the first women Lok Sabha MP to be elected from the three constituencies in Bangalore Urban.¹⁹

V – CONCLUSION:

Women's participation in societal political matters has long been viewed as a civic responsibility. Individuals in democratic societies participate in their political systems because they believe it is a moral obligation to do so. Future society will not advance until women are fully utilized. Failure to do

so is like to running a race with just one leg or thinking with only half of one's brain. Quotas for women are being allocated by governments and political parties around the world to encourage their political involvement. Women's active political participation will vastly improve present politics. Once women's participation reaches equal, conventional male-centered politics marked by authority will emerge. Work to eliminate hurdles to women's political participation, such as patriarchy, violence, money, cultural barriers and religious barriers. As a result, women should actively participate in politics to make a difference in any society.

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COMPULSORY VOTING IN INDIA: A CRITICAL EXAMINATION OF PUBLIC OPINION**Mahendra A C***Assistant Professor of Political Science, Government First Grade College, K R Pete, Mandya**Dist-571426 Mail_ siri.mahendra555@gmail.com Mob No: 9902680808*

Abstract

Compulsory voting, a widely debated electoral reform, holds significant implications for democracy by seeking to increase voter turnout. India's electoral landscape, marked by fluctuating participation rates, presents an intriguing case for examining this concept. Through a structured survey across four Lok Sabha constituencies—Bangalore Central, Mysore, Raichur, and Gulbarga—this study evaluates public opinion on compulsory voting, offering insight into the broader democratic discourse on civic duty and individual rights. The results show diverse perspectives, with a notable proportion supporting compulsory voting as a remedy for political disengagement. This article critically explores the potential benefits and challenges of implementing compulsory voting in India, referencing legal frameworks, views from the judiciary, and insights from political scholars.

Keywords: *Compulsory voting, India, electoral reform, voter turnout, democracy, public opinion*

Introduction

Compulsory voting has been enacted in numerous countries to combat low voter turnout and foster more inclusive political representation. Proponents argue it mitigates political apathy, while critics suggest it infringes upon individual freedoms (Birch, 2009; Hill & Louth, 2016). India's democratic framework recognizes voting as a fundamental right, but electoral participation varies significantly across constituencies, as evidenced in recent Lok Sabha elections (Law Commission of India, 2015). This article seeks to assess the feasibility and public perception of compulsory voting in India through empirical survey data and insights from political and legal scholars.

Literature Review

A comparative analysis of global practices reveals mixed results regarding compulsory voting's effectiveness. In Australia, for instance, compulsory voting has ensured consistently high voter turnout (Mackerras & McAllister, 1999). However, researchers like Siaroff (2000) highlight that compulsory voting alone does not ensure active civic engagement or political awareness. Similarly, Lijphart (1997) warns of unequal participation when structural issues are unaddressed. While some legal experts argue for a civic duty-based approach, the Indian judiciary maintains that voting must remain a voluntary right under constitutional frameworks (Supreme Court of India, 2015). Studies by Singh (2019) and Yadav and Palshikar (2009) underscore that socio-demographic factors like literacy, caste, and socioeconomic status significantly affect turnout, raising questions about whether compulsory voting could realistically address these disparities.

Methodology

This study utilized a structured questionnaire to collect data from 640 respondents across four Lok Sabha constituencies (Bangalore Central, Mysore, Raichur, and Gulbarga), each comprising three assembly constituencies. Survey respondents were randomly selected, and questions focused on their views regarding compulsory voting and voter turnout in the 2019 and 2024 Lok Sabha elections. Out of the 688 collected samples, 640 were retained for analysis, with approximately 390 voters reporting participation and 350 abstaining. This approach enabled us to gauge public sentiment across diverse socio-political backgrounds within the chosen constituencies.

Analysis

Survey data reveal a spectrum of attitudes toward compulsory voting. Approximately 63.6% of respondents perceive it as a favorable idea, with 41.8% endorsing it as a "Good Idea" and 21.8% as a "Very Good Idea." This indicates a substantial endorsement for compulsory voting as a mechanism to increase voter turnout in India, particularly among those concerned about political disengagement. Conversely, 29.5% express opposition, with 17.4% seeing it as a "Very Poor Idea" and 12.1% as a "Poor Idea." This opposition likely stems from concerns about autonomy and the challenges of enforcing voting mandates.

Legal perspectives provide essential context for these findings. The Law Commission of India (2015) has acknowledged the potential benefits of compulsory voting but emphasizes that any legislative attempt must be reconciled with the constitutional right to freedom of expression. Additionally, Supreme Court judgments have reinforced the voluntary nature of voting as integral to India's democratic ethos, highlighting the need for a cautious approach to mandating electoral participation (Supreme Court of India, 2015).

Comparative Analysis: Global Perspectives

Countries like Australia, Belgium, and Brazil have implemented compulsory voting with varying degrees of success. In Australia, compulsory voting has helped maintain high voter turnout rates, often above 90%. Belgium also reports strong turnout, attributing it partly to compulsory voting laws combined with accessible voting options (Hill & Sayers, 2010). In Brazil, mandatory voting is seen as part of the social contract, fostering a culture of participation despite socioeconomic challenges. However, these nations have tailored frameworks that support compulsory voting through consistent enforcement and public acceptance, factors that might be challenging to replicate in India.

Discussion

The mixed public opinion on compulsory voting in India reflects broader democratic concerns. Scholars like Blais and Dobrzynska (1998) suggest that while compulsory voting can increase turnout, it does not guarantee genuine political engagement. Critics argue that making voting mandatory without addressing root causes of apathy and disillusionment risks fostering resentment rather than civic pride. For example, India's demographic diversity, including variances in literacy, economic status, and political awareness, presents unique barriers to enforcing compulsory voting effectively (Singh, 2019). The economic and logistical feasibility of implementing such a law across India's vast and varied electorate further complicates this debate (IDEA, 2009).

Discussion: Feasibility in India

While the data suggests a favorable public opinion towards compulsory voting, the logistical and ethical challenges cannot be ignored. Implementing compulsory voting in India would require extensive legal reform, public awareness, and infrastructure improvements to make voting accessible and fair for all citizens. Moreover, the concept of compulsory voting may face resistance in India's multicultural society, where voting preferences and political participation are deeply tied to individual beliefs, socioeconomic conditions, and regional differences.

Conclusion

The data highlights a divided stance on compulsory voting among Indian voters. While a majority favors it as a tool to counter low turnout, significant concerns about freedom, enforceability, and addressing the underlying causes of political disengagement remain. Legal and constitutional perspectives underscore that any move towards compulsory voting must be delicately balanced with democratic freedoms. As India continues to explore electoral reforms, a nuanced approach that emphasizes voter

education, accessible polling, and civic responsibility over mandates may better align with the country's democratic principles and foster genuine electoral participation.

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CONSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR SUSTAINABLE GOVERNANCE IN INDIA: AN ANALYSIS

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Abstract

A strong foundation for sustainable government is offered by the Indian Constitution, which is the ultimate law of the land. Social, economic, and environmental aspects of governance are incorporated into the Constitution through its Preamble, Directive Principles of State Policy, and Fundamental Rights. The state and its residents are required under the Constitution to preserve and enhance the environment, which promotes sustainable development. By virtue of its interpretations, the judiciary has reaffirmed this commitment, making sustainable governance a legal requirement rather than only an ideal.

The Constitution performs a vital part in fostering sustainability because it strikes a balance between social justice, economic growth, and environmental preservation, ensuring that development does not jeopardize the requirements of future generations. The Indian Constitution upholds the rights of all citizens, guarantees equality, and protects vulnerable groups, all of which serve to advance social justice. Substantial contribution to the advancement of economic growth by means of its numerous provisions, which lay the groundwork for an equitable and inclusive economy.

The Indian Constitution provides a complete framework that prioritizes accountability, transparency, the rule of law, and the separation of powers in order to foster good governance and efficient administration. This is how the Constitution encourages efficient administration and government. However, the stability of state governance and the security of our constitution demonstrate what social fairness and economic progress India has made.

Key Words: *Constitution, Sustainable, Governance, Separation of Power, Judiciary, Government.*

Introduction

The Indian Constitution plays a crucial role in ensuring administrative stability by providing a clear framework for governance, legal authority, and institutional checks and balances. It establishes a federal structure, dividing powers between the central and state governments, allowing for both national coherence and regional autonomy. This helps prevent conflicts and ensures smooth functioning across various levels of administration. The Constitution also creates an independent judiciary, which ensures that laws and executive actions remain constitutional. This system of judicial review checks arbitrary decisions and promotes lawful administration. Additionally, the Constitution sets up independent institutions like the Election Commission, Comptroller and Auditor General (CAG), and Public Service Commissions, which promote transparency, accountability, and continuity in governance. By outlining fundamental rights, duties, and principles such as equality before the law, the Constitution ensures that the administrative machinery operates fairly, providing citizens with legal recourse against governmental excesses. The amendment process allows the Constitution to evolve while maintaining stability, ensuring that governance remains relevant and responsive to changing circumstances.¹

Constitutionalism in the Indian Administrative System.

The Constitution declares India as a sovereign, socialist, secular, and democratic republic, ensuring that power is derived from the people. This is reflected in its preamble, which encapsulates the ideals of liberty, equality, and fraternity. The democratic essence is also guaranteed by the fundamental rights granted to all citizens, allowing them to freely express their opinions, participate in governance, and elect their representatives.² Through periodic elections, citizens actively shape the country's political system. The Election Commission, an independent constitutional authority, is tasked with conducting

free and fair elections, thereby ensuring the integrity of the democratic process. The principle of universal adult suffrage grants every citizen, irrespective of caste, creed, religion, or gender, the right to vote, reinforcing the democratic ethos enshrined in the Constitution.

A vital feature of the Indian Constitution is the separation of powers among the legislature, executive, and judiciary. This system of checks and balances ensures that no branch of government wields unchecked authority, thus maintaining the democratic fabric. The legislature, composed of elected representatives, enacts laws; the executive implements these laws; and the judiciary interprets and upholds them. The judiciary, in particular, plays a crucial role in protecting the Constitution and democratic principles. Through the power of judicial review, the Supreme Court of India has the authority to declare laws or executive actions unconstitutional if they violate any provision of the Constitution. This ensures that all political and legal actions remain within the bounds of constitutional propriety.

The Indian Constitution establishes a federal system with a strong central government. It divides powers between the Union and State governments through three distinct lists: The Union List, State List, and Concurrent List. This division balances the need for central authority with regional autonomy, ensuring that local governments have the flexibility to address the specific needs of their constituencies. The Constitution also provides mechanisms to resolve disputes between the Union and the states, fostering cooperation within a diverse and large country. The institution of Panchayati Raj and municipalities also empowers local governance, allowing for democratic decision-making at the grassroots level. This decentralization of power protects democracy by making governance more inclusive and responsive to the needs of the people.³

The protection of individual rights is one of the bedrocks of Indian democracy. The Constitution enshrines Fundamental Rights in Part III, ensuring that every citizen has the right to freedom of speech, expression, assembly, and association. These rights protect individuals from arbitrary actions of the state and allow for healthy political discourse. Citizens can criticize government policies, form political parties, and participate in peaceful protests without fear of repression. At the same time, the Constitution also imposes Fundamental Duties on citizens, which are meant to promote a sense of responsibility and contribute to the nation's democratic ideals. The duties encourage citizens to uphold the Constitution, respect its institutions, and foster a spirit of tolerance and harmony.

India is a diverse country with a multitude of cultures, languages, religions, and social structures. To protect this diversity within the framework of democracy, the Constitution provides specific safeguards for vulnerable and marginalized communities. Reservation policies for Scheduled Castes (SCs), Scheduled Tribes (STs), and Other Backward Classes (OBCs) in legislatures, educational institutions, and government jobs ensure their political representation and socio-economic advancement.⁴ The Constitution also upholds secularism by maintaining a delicate balance between the state and religion. The state is prohibited from favouring or discriminating against any religion, ensuring equal treatment of all religious communities, which fosters social harmony and political stability.

The Indian Constitution is a living document capable of evolving over time. The amendment process allows the Constitution to adapt to changing political, social, and economic conditions. The Constitution can be amended by Parliament under Article 368, ensuring that it remains relevant while preserving its core democratic values.⁵

However, the basic structure of the Constitution, as elucidated by the Supreme Court in the Kesavananda Bharati case (1973), cannot be altered, ensuring that the fundamental democratic

principles remain intact. This doctrine of the basic structure ensures that the Constitution can evolve while preventing any drastic changes that could undermine democracy.⁶

Several independent institutions are established by the Constitution to safeguard the democratic process. Apart from the Election Commission, bodies such as the Comptroller and Auditor General of India (CAG), the Public Service Commissions, and the Finance Commission play significant roles in ensuring transparency and accountability in governance. Furthermore, civil liberties such as the freedom of the press, access to information through the Right to Information Act, and the functioning of civil society organizations provide the necessary checks on political power.⁷ These institutions and rights enable citizens to hold their representatives accountable and strengthen India's democratic framework. The Indian Constitution is a formidable protector of democracy, ensuring that political power is vested in the people and exercised through democratic institutions. By upholding the principles of equality, justice, and individual freedoms, the Constitution safeguards Indian politics against authoritarianism, corruption, and injustice. Its system of checks and balances, the protection of fundamental rights, the promotion of federalism, and the establishment of independent institutions contribute to a vibrant and resilient democratic system. The Constitution of India not only protects Indian politics but also ensures that democracy flourishes in one of the most diverse nations in the world.

Sustainable administration refers to a governance model that ensures efficient, transparent, and accountable functioning of public institutions while fostering long-term, equitable development. The Indian Constitution provides a foundational framework that emphasizes the need for sustainability in governance through various principles and provisions, ensuring that administrative actions are both responsive to the current needs and capable of preserving resources for future generations.

This article explores how the Indian Constitution envisions sustainable administration by examining key constitutional provisions related to transparency, accountability, decentralization, and the balance between development and environmental stewardship.

Separation of Powers and Checks and Balances:

One of the core pillars of sustainable administration in the Indian Constitution is the doctrine of separation of powers between the legislature, executive, and judiciary. This ensures that no single branch of government accumulates excessive power, thus maintaining a system of checks and balances essential for long-term sustainability in governance.⁸

Article 50: This article directs the state to separate the judiciary from the executive in the public services of the state. The independence of the judiciary allows it to act as a guardian of the Constitution, ensuring that administrative actions are lawful and just. Judicial Review (Article 13): Through the power of judicial review, the courts can nullify laws and administrative actions that violate the Constitution. This is a critical tool for promoting sustainable administration, ensuring that government actions do not undermine citizens' rights or breach constitutional mandates. The judiciary acts as a check on executive overreach, which is essential for sustainable governance.

Fundamental Rights and Administrative Accountability:

The Indian Constitution provides a set of Fundamental Rights (Part III), which not only empower citizens but also impose limitations on the powers of the administration. These rights play a crucial role in promoting transparency, accountability, and fairness in administrative actions.⁹

Article 14 (Right to Equality): This article ensures equality before the law and equal protection of the laws, preventing arbitrary or discriminatory actions by the administration. By mandating that administrative actions must be fair and reasonable, Article 14 lays the groundwork for sustainable governance that treats all citizens equitably. Article 21 (Right to Life and Personal Liberty): Judicial

interpretation of Article 21 has expanded its scope to include the right to a dignified life, clean environment, and protection from arbitrary state actions. The judiciary has invoked Article 21 to ensure that the state's administrative decisions take into account the health, well-being, and rights of citizens. Right to Information (RTI Act, 2005): Though not explicitly part of the original Constitution, the RTI Act is a reflection of constitutional values. It stems from Article 19(1)(a) (Right to Freedom of Speech and Expression), ensuring transparency in administration by allowing citizens to seek information about government activities.¹⁰ Access to information is crucial for sustainable administration as it empowers citizens to hold the administration accountable.

Directive Principles of State Policy (DPSP):

The Directive Principles of State Policy (Part IV) guide the state in formulating policies and laws that ensure sustainable development and administration. While these principles are not enforceable by courts, they are fundamental in the governance of the country.

Article 38: The state is directed to promote the welfare of the people by securing a social order in which justice—social, economic, and political—shall inform all institutions of national life. This implies that the administration must work towards reducing inequalities, promoting welfare, and ensuring that development reaches all sections of society sustainably. Article 39(b) & (c): These articles guide the state to ensure that the ownership and control of material resources are distributed to subserve the common good and that the economic system does not result in the concentration of wealth. This fosters a sustainable administration that prioritizes equitable resource distribution and inclusive economic growth. Article 47: The state is directed to improve public health, which implies the need for long-term strategies in the areas of healthcare, sanitation, and the environment. Sustainable administration in this context includes creating policies that promote the health and well-being of citizens, ensuring that administrative decisions do not compromise public health for short-term gains.

Environmental Protection and Sustainability:

The Indian Constitution envisions a sustainable administrative framework that balances economic development with environmental protection, ensuring that the nation's natural resources are preserved for future generations. Article 48-A: Added through the 42nd Amendment, Article 48-A states that "the State shall endeavour to protect and improve the environment and to safeguard the forests and wildlife of the country." This provision requires the administration to integrate environmental concerns into their governance processes and policy-making, ensuring sustainable use of natural resources. Article 51-A(g) (Fundamental Duties): This article emphasizes the duty of every citizen to protect and improve the natural environment. Though directed at citizens, it also implies that the administration must create mechanisms that enable and encourage citizens to fulfil this duty. Sustainable administration must thus prioritize environmental education, awareness, and citizen engagement.

Decentralization and Grassroots Governance:

A key feature of sustainable administration is the empowerment of local self-governance through decentralization. The 73rd and 74th Amendments to the Constitution introduced Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) and urban local bodies, making local governments constitutionally recognized entities. Articles 243 to 243-O (Panchayats) and Articles 243-P to 243-ZG (Municipalities): These provisions ensure that local governments have administrative powers and financial autonomy, allowing them to make decisions suited to local needs. Decentralization is crucial for sustainable administration, as it enables local participation in governance, ensures accountability at the grassroots level, and allows for the tailoring of policies to specific regional conditions. Decentralized Resource Management: Sustainable administration at the local level also involves empowering these local bodies to manage

natural resources water, forests, and land more efficiently, ensuring their use does not exceed their capacity for regeneration.¹¹

Service Delivery and Good Governance:

A sustainable administration must also focus on efficient service delivery, ensuring that basic amenities healthcare, education, water, and sanitation reach all citizens in an equitable manner. The Indian Constitution, through various provisions, promotes good governance practices that enhance the efficiency and responsiveness of the administration.¹²

Social Welfare and Inclusive Growth: The Directive Principles, particularly Articles 41 (Right to work, education, and public assistance), 42 (Provision for just and humane conditions of work), and 47 (Duty of the State to raise the level of nutrition and the standard of living), mandate the state to create welfare policies that cater to the most vulnerable sections of society.¹³ Sustainable administration ensures that these services are delivered efficiently, without exclusion or bias.

Conclusion

The Indian Constitution, through its emphasis on transparency, accountability, environmental protection, decentralization, and inclusive growth, provides a comprehensive framework for sustainable administration. The balance between the rights of citizens, the duties of the state, and the need for long-term environmental and social equity is enshrined in various constitutional provisions. Over the decades, the judiciary, legislature, and executive have worked together to interpret and implement these principles, ensuring that India's administrative machinery evolves to meet the challenges of sustainable governance in a complex, diverse society

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AN ANALYSIS OF POLITICAL PARTICIPATION OF WOMEN IN PANCHAYAT RAJ INSTITUTIONS OF RURAL INDIA

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Abstract

Democracy is a political system, based on representative government, the people's participation in the political process, freedoms for citizens, transparency of political acts and process. The political participation was another notion of true democracy. The Women constitutes more than half of the world population and their contribution to the social and economic development of society is more than half as compared to that of men by virtue of their dual roles in the productive and reproductive spheres. In compared to men, women continue to be under-represented as voters, leaders, and as elected members at the Political level. As a result, women do not have equal influence over the policy decisions that affect their lives. In this context, the Political empowerment of women through Political Participation in Panchayat Raj institutions remains to be a big challenge in India. This paper examines the political Participation of women in India with reference to Women's participation in Panchayat Raj institutions of rural India with various indicators.

Keywords: *Women, Political participation, Empowerment, Gender Equality, Panchayat Raj institutions, 73rd Amendment, Democratic decentralization.*

INTRODUCTION:

The Women in India had been seen many difficulties since the ancient times. They had lived as an oppressed class in the society. Nevertheless, after independence, in India the status of women regained its strength and vigor in almost all types of economic activities and in active politics. Nevertheless, women's participation in decision-making positions is a biggest challenge today. In India, Panchyati Raj Institutions to good governance and in this direction the 73rd Constitutional Amendment to the constitution for better governance and to provide political power to Women and disadvantaged section of the society. In the political level, there is a growing momentum among governments to foster and ensure women's participation in Panchayat governance structures. Establishing quotas for women's representation at Different levels of governance has been a strategic tactic of achieving the goal in many countries. The common factors identified as barriers to women's participation include the gender-based discrimination, personal obstacles such as lack of confidence, culturally prescribed domestic roles, low voter education and lack of financial and socio-economic capital.

POLITICAL PARTICIPATION OF WOMEN IN PANCHAYAT RAJ INSTITUTIONS OF RURAL INDIA:

The political Empowerment of Women in Panchayats means participation of Women in Political decision making at grass root level. In ancient India, The Panchayats means an elected council with executive and judicial powers in ancient India. Historically, the Mughals and the British brought fundamental socio-economic and structural changes in Panchayat Raj level. The Lord Ripon towards the end of the nineteenth century brought the importance of local governance to the forefront. A resolution has made in 1882 for the establishment of local boards. This repeated in 1909 in the report of the Royal Commission on Decentralization. As a result, rural district boards and village Panchayats were set up. But, in the first set of Panchayat Acts that came in 1920s in the then provinces and princely states where women had not figured either as representatives or even as voters.

The important factors that hinder women's political participation in Panchayats of rural India include male domination in politics, political parties, and culture of political structures. The male dominated political parties have a male perspective on issues of national importance. The larger democratic framework and level of democratization also affects women's political participation. Political activism and voting are the strongest areas of women's political participation. To combat gender inequality in politics, the Indian Government has instituted reservations for seats in Panchayat level.

In the political sphere, many factors limit the active engagement of women. These include, firstly, the deeply rooted stereotype norms relegate women to the domestic space with severely restricted engagement in public affairs, and men dominated this area. Secondly, caste and class restrictions and the patriarchal system and mindset pervade the political space provided to women. Women not recognized as political entities and their perspective as integral to the design and delivery of services. The third factor is the lack of exposure of women themselves to politics and the absence of any experience in exercising their political responsibilities. Low literacy levels, absence of education and limited or no exposure, all lead to a lack of confidence and many women are unable to comprehend the true spirit of decentralization and recognize the opportunities that it provides. The Non-participation of the population and especially of women in Panchayat institutions, despite over half a century of experimentation, remained a major concern of those who would like to see democratic traditions getting strong.

A parliamentary system of government was enshrined in the Indian Constitution and guarantees its citizens the right to elect, freedom of speech, freedom to assemble and form associations, and vote. The Constitution of India attempts to remove gender inequalities by banning discrimination based on sex and class, prohibiting human trafficking and forced labour, and reserving elected positions for women. The Government of India has directed state and local governments to promote equality by class and gender including equal pay and free legal aid, humane working conditions and maternity relief, right to work and education, and raising the standard of living.

The concept of gender equality was included in the form of constitutional rights after Indian Independence. But, however, women continue to be under-represented in legislative bodies. In this scenario, the participatory upsurge witnessed among women as voters in the 1990s reached its peak in the general election held in 2024. Their participation in the electoral process as voters has steadily increased from 46.6 percent in 1962 to around 65.7 percent in 2024. The difference in voter turnout among men and women, as wide as 16.7 percent in 1962, has narrowed to 1.5 percent in 2024. We can say that the main reason for this upward trend was due to the fact that, 33 percent seats for women in Panchayat in the 1990s gave women a sense of sharing power with men equally. This finally resulted in the upsurge of women voters.

In the Indian constitution, the affirmative action by reservation of seats for women and disadvantaged sections of the society was enshrined through 73rd Amendment Act, 1992. This act calls for the reservation of a minimum of one-third of seats for women in locally elected governance bodies. In 2009, the Government of India approved a 50 percent reservation for women in Panchayats and many states have passed similar legislation. The same amendment also calls for Panchayats to prepare and implement plans for economic development and social justice. The Affirmative action to ensure women's political representation is an important step in democratising and engendering Panchayats governance. At the institutional level, the capacity of local structures to implement reforms, institutionalise accountability systems, decentralise functions and facilitate women's active engagement

plays a role in determining whether women are able to emerge as political agents and actors. The social barriers include lack of education, lack of respect for women in Panchayats, physical violence against women in the public and domestic spheres as well as oppressive patriarchal and caste structures. The Traditional power hierarchies in favour of men and it resist giving space or recognition to women's attempts to be part of the political scenario.

CONCLUSION:

Overall, it sought to present the nature and extent of Women's political participation in India with reference to Women participation in panchayat raj institutions of rural India. It focused both on parliamentary politics and Women empowerment through the political representation. The extension of Women political representation positions is one of most challenging government issues in the century. In spite of the fact that women gained consistent political ground, also considerable variety exists regarding the development and change in the society. The political participation means, the correlation between the political system and level of women participation in the political life. In rural India, the only positive aspect in the dark clouds hovering over women's participation in politics has been the marked increase in voting turnout among women. The women's movement and gender politics in rural India today divided over the question of women Political Participation in Panchayat level. Thus, a positive action for women in Panchayats is the need of the hour, as it would go a long way in removing obstacles that inhibit their participation in Panchayat level. It would bridge the wide men-women gap in the electoral set-up and pave the way for gender-inclusive electoral politics.

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CULTURAL DIVERSITY AND NATIONAL UNITY IN INDIA: AN ANALYSIS**Dr. Mouneshwara Srinivasrao**

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Abstract

India is a vast and multifaceted nation known for its rich cultural diversity, with an array of languages, religions, ethnicities, and traditions. Despite this immense diversity, India has retained a sense of national unity, albeit with challenges. This paper explores the dimensions of India's cultural diversity, the historical and socio-political forces shaping unity, and the challenges and opportunities for national integration in a diverse society. Using a blend of historical and sociological analysis, this research highlights the importance of a pluralistic approach in sustaining national unity and offers recommendations for fostering greater harmony within this cultural mosaic. And also aims to analyze the elements of cultural diversity and examine the mechanisms that have contributed to national unity in India, as well as the challenges that have emerged over time.

Keywords: Cultural Diversity, National Unity, Ethnic Groups, Indian Constitution, Secularism, Regionalism, National Integration, Inclusive Development

1. Introduction:

India's identity is defined by its diversity, which encompasses not only ethnic and linguistic groups but also a multiplicity of religions, traditions, and social practices. This diversity has been both a source of strength and a challenge for the country. While the diversity fosters a vibrant culture and societal resilience, it also poses challenges to national unity. Understanding how India has historically managed to maintain unity in diversity is essential for formulating strategies for a peaceful and integrated future.

India, often described as a “subcontinent” due to its geographical, cultural, and demographic diversity, is a nation that embodies an unparalleled blend of ethnicities, languages, religions, and traditions. Stretching across 3.287 million square kilometers, with over 1.3 billion people, India is home to some of the oldest and most intricate cultures in human history. This vast diversity, however, presents both immense opportunities and formidable challenges for the nation.

Cultural diversity in India is not merely a byproduct of geography; it is deeply intertwined with the nation's historical evolution and social framework. This diversity is evident in every aspect of life, from the hundreds of dialects spoken across different regions to the religious beliefs and festivals celebrated throughout the year. With 22 officially recognized languages and countless ethnic groups, India's societal structure reflects a mosaic of cultural identities that, while distinct, contribute collectively to the Indian ethos. Moreover, India's multiplicity extends beyond mere language or religion—it includes food habits, dress styles, social customs, and even philosophical beliefs. Each community's contributions, from traditional art forms to literature and music, enrich the broader culture, making diversity a valuable asset to India's collective identity.

The concept of “unity in diversity” has become a defining characteristic of the Indian national identity, symbolizing a resilient sense of togetherness amid diverse identities. This unity, however, is not simply organic but is cultivated through historical and social processes. Unlike homogeneous societies, India's path to unity has been complex, involving the continuous negotiation of cultural, linguistic, and religious differences. National unity is thus not a static ideal but a dynamic process that requires collective will and systemic support.

Historically, India's diverse regions have faced the challenge of harmonizing local and regional identities with a broader national identity. These challenges were exacerbated during colonial rule, when divisions were often exploited to weaken collective Indian opposition. However, in response, leaders of the Indian freedom struggle embraced the ideal of a unified nation that would respect and celebrate diversity. This idea was institutionalized in the post-independence period, with the Indian Constitution enshrining principles of secularism, federalism, and linguistic autonomy to promote inclusivity and unity.

While cultural diversity contributes to India's richness, it also poses challenges to social cohesion and national unity. Differences in regional economic development, religious tensions, and linguistic rivalries have at times led to conflicts that threaten India's social fabric. Regionalism, communalism, and separatist movements have posed recurrent threats to national unity. In recent years, socio-political changes, globalization, and technological advances have intensified identity-based mobilizations, increasing the need for a nuanced understanding of the balance between diversity and unity.

The purpose of this paper is to analyze how India has managed to maintain a unified national identity amid significant diversity. It seeks to examine both the historical roots of India's unity and the socio-political frameworks that continue to support it, particularly the role of the Indian Constitution. Additionally, this study explores the contemporary challenges to national integration and offers recommendations to foster unity within this diverse society. By understanding the factors that facilitate and challenge unity in diversity, this analysis aims to contribute to the broader discourse on national integration in multicultural societies.

2. Dimensions of Cultural Diversity in India:

India is one of the most culturally diverse nations in the world, characterized by:

2.1 Ethnic and Linguistic Diversity

India is home to over 2,000 distinct ethnic groups and more than 1,600 spoken languages. The 22 officially recognized languages in the Eighth Schedule of the Indian Constitution reflect the linguistic diversity of the nation, while hundreds of regional dialects add further complexity to this tapestry¹. Major linguistic families in India include Indo-Aryan, Dravidian, Austroasiatic, and Tibeto-Burman. This linguistic variety forms the bedrock of India's cultural identity.

2.2 Religious Diversity

India has been the birthplace of several major religions, including Hinduism, Buddhism, Jainism, and Sikhism. Additionally, Islam, Christianity, Zoroastrianism, and Judaism have also become integral parts of the religious landscape. Each religious group has brought unique cultural practices, festivals, and worldviews, contributing to a rich religious diversity that is celebrated through a plethora of festivals, rituals, and traditions².

2.3 Regional and Traditional Diversity

India's diversity is also visible in its regional practices, clothing, cuisine, art forms, and architecture. Each state and region has distinct cultural identities, traditions, and social norms, shaped by geography, historical factors, and external influences. For instance, the dance forms of Bharatnatyam in Tamil Nadu, Kathakali in Kerala and Kathak in northern India each represent a distinct cultural heritage tied to specific regions³.

3. Historical Foundations of National Unity:

Despite these diversities, a sense of national unity has historically emerged through shared experiences and collective identity:

3.1 Influence of Ancient Empires

Ancient Indian empires, such as the Maurya and Gupta dynasties, contributed to the early unification of diverse regions by implementing administrative policies and creating trade networks that linked various cultural groups. The spread of Buddhism and Jainism during these eras also fostered a shared philosophical and ethical foundation, contributing to cultural synthesis⁴.

3.2 The Mughal Empire and Syncretism

The Mughal Empire, especially under Akbar's rule, encouraged cultural syncretism by promoting inter-religious dialogue and incorporating diverse traditions within the royal court. Akbar's policy of "Sulh-i-Kul" (universal peace) established a framework of religious tolerance and interfaith respect, fostering a sense of unity among diverse groups⁵.

3.3 Colonial Rule and the Freedom Struggle

The British colonization of India paradoxically fostered a sense of national unity as diverse groups united against a common foreign oppressor. The Indian National Congress, founded in 1885, became a platform for the masses, regardless of regional, religious, or linguistic identity, to demand independence. Leaders like Mahatma Gandhi emphasized inclusive nationalism, advocating for unity in diversity as a foundational principle for an independent India⁶.

4. Role of the Indian Constitution in Promoting Unity in Diversity:

The Indian Constitution, adopted in 1950, has been instrumental in ensuring that diversity is recognized and respected within the framework of national unity.

4.1 Secularism and Religious Freedom

India's secular framework guarantees all citizens the freedom to practice and propagate their religion without interference. This constitutional secularism provides a basis for harmonious coexistence and respects the cultural autonomy of religious groups, thereby facilitating national unity amid diversity⁷.

4.2 Linguistic Policy

To accommodate linguistic diversity, the Constitution does not impose any one language as the national language. Instead, Hindi and English are recognized as official languages for central government purposes, while states have the freedom to choose their own official languages. This flexible language policy has prevented linguistic domination and contributed to national unity by respecting regional identities⁸.

4.3 Protective Policies for Minority Groups

The Constitution includes provisions for the protection of cultural, educational, and linguistic rights of minorities. Articles 29 and 30, for instance, provide minorities with the right to establish and administer educational institutions of their choice, thereby promoting inclusivity and reducing potential friction among different cultural groups⁹.

5. Challenges to National Unity in a Diverse Society:

5.1 Regionalism and Ethnic Tensions

India has witnessed ethnic and regional tensions, often fueled by perceived inequalities in resource distribution and political representation. Movements for statehood based on linguistic or ethnic identity, such as the creation of Telangana, reflect the challenges of balancing regional aspirations with national interests¹⁰.

5.2 Religious Polarization

Religious polarization and communal conflicts have challenged India's national unity. Incidents of communal violence and the rise of majoritarian ideologies can undermine inter-community trust and create divisions that threaten the country's secular fabric¹¹.

5.3 Economic Disparities

Economic inequality is another factor that impacts national unity. Disparities in income, access to resources, and economic opportunities between various regions and communities contribute to social tension and often manifest as regional or communal grievances, which can erode social cohesion¹².

6. Opportunities for Strengthening National Unity:

6.1 Promoting Intercultural Dialogue

Educational and cultural programs that promote interfaith and intercultural dialogue can enhance understanding and reduce prejudices among communities. The role of institutions such as the National Integration Council in promoting mutual respect and understanding should be strengthened¹³.

6.2 Decentralization and Local Governance

Decentralization can empower local governance, allowing communities to address their needs while being part of the broader national framework. Strengthening panchayats and urban local bodies promotes a sense of participation and ownership, which can contribute to national integration¹⁴.

6.3 Inclusive Economic Development

Ensuring equitable economic growth across all regions can mitigate socio-economic disparities and foster unity. Investment in underserved regions, alongside affirmative action policies, can contribute to a more inclusive society where diverse communities feel valued and integrated¹⁵.

7. Conclusion:

India's unity in diversity is a testament to its resilience as a nation that celebrates pluralism. The Indian Constitution, historical influences, and cultural adaptability have provided the foundation for a society that respects diversity while promoting national unity. However, the journey is ongoing, and challenges such as regionalism, religious polarization, and economic disparities continue to test this unity. By fostering intercultural understanding, inclusive economic growth, and equitable policies, India can further strengthen its national unity amid cultural diversity.

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DEMOCRACY'S NEW GUARD: YOUTH, IDENTITY, AND POLITICAL RENEWAL IN CONTEMPORARY INDIA

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Abstract

Examining the evolving landscape of youth political participation in India's democratic framework, focusing on the intersection of identity politics & Pluralism, initiatives and action plan

Indian democracy, the world's largest, is a beacon of pluralism yet also a battleground for identity-based politics. Elections frequently hinge on divisive issues, with campaigns often sidelining key matters like employment, education, and social justice. However, India's youth—comprising nearly half the population—represent a powerful force capable of shifting the political discourse. This article explores the role of youth in reshaping India's democratic framework by moving from identity/Pluralism-driven to development-focused politics. Analysing factors contributing to identity politics, the potential impact of youth, current initiatives promoting youth engagement, and the role of youth-led movements, this paper identifies pathways to foster a more inclusive, progressive democratic landscape for India.

Introduction

India's democratic ethos, celebrated for its size and diversity, faces critical challenges due to the rise of identity politics. Political parties often leverage caste, religion, and regional loyalties to consolidate support, overshadowing core developmental issues. Despite high voter turnout, 46% of India's youth population expresses limited interest in politics, with few holding strong political affiliations. Given that youth represent 49% of India's population, their engagement is crucial to redirect India's democracy towards inclusive, policy-driven governance. Youth involvement could transform India's political discourse, bringing fresh perspectives and solutions to developmental challenges, including social justice, education, and employment.

This study aims to address the following research questions:

- What are the primary factors contributing to the prevalence of identity politics in Indian democracy?
- How can youth engagement transform the current political landscape from identity-based to development-focused?
- What are the steps taken by Government to maximise youth in Politics?
- What initiatives and strategies are most effective in fostering meaningful political participation among Indian youth?

Challenges of Identity Politics in Indian Democracy

1. Caste-Based Vote Banks: Most political actors associate themselves with one form of caste organizations to garner support relegating developmental ideologies. Caste based representation is otherwise progressive as it represents the interest of suppressed class and yet it strengthens the divide.
2. Religious Nationalism: There is tendency for religious affiliations to being employed as tools of mobilization, this at the expense of secularism. This has inevitably perpetuated divide and rule mentality in communities so much that their attention is shifted from development.
3. Regionalism and Language: Ethnolinguistic classifications continue to be significant, particularly in state level contests, where references to regional culture and language may polarize the nation.

4. Lack of Developmental Narratives: Since identity is such a powerful political tool, it makes politicians steer clear of policy debates and thereby setting little space for economic or social change even during election times.

All these factors explain why in the current political environment developmental needs do not receive the deserved attention and democracy thus becomes a mechanism that hampers progress and participation by the populace.

Youth Participation & Representation in Indian Politics

Source : Worldbank data accessed for population distribution & Election Commission website for MPs age in 18th Loksabha elections.

Key Findings:

- Young adults (18-39 years) constitute 61.62% of the voting-age population
- Young MPs (25-39) represent only 8.84% of parliament despite eligible young population being 61.6% of voting population.
- This creates a massive representation gap of 52.78 percentage points between youth population (61.62%) and youth MPs (8.84%)
- Most MPs (91.16%) are 40 years or older, representing only 38.38% of the population

Youth-Led Movements in India

A plethora of youths has actively participated in shaping the India population socio-politically, with the splendid demonstration of the actual power of youths. The Chipko Movement of the 1970s was an action in which young villagers of Uttarakhand physically lodged themselves around the trees to prevent extensive felling of trees and gave an importance to the cause of the environment. In 2011, coming back again to assert the Jan Lokpal Bill as the idea of Anti-Corruption Movement led by Anna Hazare got itself huge youths support to pass the bill. The second such movement was the Nirbhaya Movement in 2012. Loud protests have happened for the brutal assault in Delhi and many youths of India came on the roads demanding justice seeking amendment in laws and stringent laws related to sexual assault cases should be passed. In 2017, youth protesters took to the streets of Tamil Nadu to protest the ban of, Jallikattu, a bull taming sport demonstrated a concern with tradition and conservation of animals. From the year 2019 to 2020, the Anti- CAA agitation held the youth of India to protest on this new created law stating citizen amendment act making the youth again concerned about secularism and citizenship rights. These movements demonstrate young people as agents of justice, accountability and equality, and how they can bring change regardless of complacent and oppressive structures.

The Change Youth Can Drive in Indian Politics

The young group of voters has the propensity to redefine the priorities of the Indian government when it comes to politics. If youths get involved in political processes, they can change the nature of politics

and politics discourse from Identity politics to development politics. For instance, if youths are advocating for something like employment; health; or injustice they can be able to pressure leaders to think of policies that concern the basic aspects of welfare. The transition from identity politics to policy discussions could be India's success and guarantee that the authorities are acting in the country's best interest. Third, youth participation automatically forces more inclusive forms of governance. Millennials especially have the culture of supporting policies that cut across the bar of the traditional social demographics. To this extent, such a shift is especially important in a condition of a multicultural social outlook like that in India, the handling of which may well be facilitated by an increased tolerance for cultural difference. Also, young voters/activists are usually active in the matters of the corrupt free society and thus acts in favor of democracy. With their indifference and demand for ethical governance, they can set the pace for responsible leadership with more concern of the public good than parochial interests. It also promotes the participation of young people to enhance leadership by ensuring a new breed of leadership in political activities. It basically means that one can enter campaigns themselves or support young and liberal people to bring spirit, creativity, and a focus on the common good into politics. This change can result in new policies that have a development connotation, rather than a division one since youth are visionary people who tend to embrace the development of everyone.

Initiatives Encouraging Youth Political Participation

There are many governmental and community-based programs and campaigns in India that encourage young people to become active participants in the political process because the authorities understand that young people should develop civility.

National Youth Policy (NYP)

The latest draft NYP envisions a ten-year development plan through 2030, focusing on five priority areas[1]:

- Education and skill development
- Employment and entrepreneurship
- Youth leadership development
- Health, fitness and sports
- Social justice

National Youth Parliament Scheme

The National Youth Parliament Scheme is a comprehensive program designed to engage Indian youth in active citizenship and leadership. [2]

The program aims to:

- Strengthen democratic roots
- Foster discipline and tolerance
- Familiarize students with parliamentary procedures
- Provide a platform for youth to voice opinions on national issues

Nehru Yuva Kendra Sangathan (NYKS)

Established in 1972, NYKS is one of the largest grassroots youth organizations globally [3].

It aims to:

- Provide rural youth opportunities for nation-building
- Channel youth energy through volunteerism
- Promote community participation
- Establish networks of village-level youth clubs

National Service Scheme (NSS)

Launched on September 24, 1969, during Mahatma Gandhi's birth centenary year[4]. The scheme operates under the motto "Not Me But You" and focuses on:

- Developing student personality through community service
- Understanding community needs
- Building civic responsibility
- Practicing national integration

National Young Leaders Programme (NYLP)

Launched in 2014-15, this comprehensive program includes five major components [6]:

- Neighbourhood Youth Parliament
- Youth for Development Programme
- National Young Leaders Awards
- National Youth Advisory Council
- National Youth Development Fund

These programs aims to develop leadership qualities among youth aged 15-29 years to enable them to realize their full potential and contribute to nation-building [6].

Essential Steps to Foster Youth Participation in Politics

For the effective youth participation in political procedures in India, following basic changes are required. Of these strategies, one that has considered as a critical is the enhancement of democracy education in learning institutions. Lesson plans should be copyright to bring out the spirit of democracy, problem solving and the synergy of diversity. Such knowledge would enable students to get a good background of how the civil issues are likely to be appreciated and to participate in politics in a meaningful manner. Thus, having these emotional and intellectual tools at their disposal, young people can engage diversity of political processes with certain understanding. In an aspect, organized political structure encompasses political parties that support the youths to vie for political power. Mentorship and supporting young candidates enable them, prepare to provide new innovative development-oriented ideas within political parties to come up thus providing for new ideas within the party platforms. Changes in electoral laws designed to call for proportional representation, campaign finance reforms would also serve to dilute the effects of identity politics by providing young reformist candidates an opportunity to running for office, and win. Besides these institutional alterations, digital advocacy skill is part of necessary skill set needed for youngsters in today's generation. Media literacy and advocacy training may make youth equipped for trusting and processing information content, debunking rumours and acting in a socially suitable manner when it comes to political activities. Encouraging communication is another key area: local programs that allow young people from different communities to discuss relevant issues is another important facet; the application of caste/religious/ regional barriers disappear when individuals are speaking directly with one another.

Pathways for Youth to Lead Change in Politics

Transforming political environment spearheaded by youths needs cooperation from different entities. Thus, if, for example, schools and NGOs enter formal partnerships, the latter develop civic engagement programs that will generate the politically sensitive generation. Such partnerships may guarantee young people get not only knowledge based on academic courses but also some information about the political process and the importance of voting. It also said that social networks are advocacy instruments and collaborating with social media companies hears young voices. In this way, the platforms free up space for issue-based narratives and thus have the potential in enabling youths to stay aligned to policy-based

politics rather than identity politics which is detrimental to the growth of a political culture of substance and ideas. In addition, incentives, which may include scholarships, internships, and funding for youth-led projects originate from government giving youth real reasons to be actively involved in politics effectively, giving them a boost in their leadership skills. Last but not the least, civil society has enormous potential for getting youths to participate through intelligent lobbying for relevant campaigns. Activity that promotes free and fair election, policy contented, and voters' responsibilities may draw youths towards voting. In this way, the generation of youngsters in India can transform their nation toward the better future in regard to the principles of development, effectiveness and openness in governance.

Conclusion

India's youth, as both its present and future, possess the potential to reshape the nation's political landscape. By moving away from identity-based politics and focusing on development, they can establish a democracy that reflects India's ideals of unity, equality, and justice. Their participation, whether through voting, advocacy, or candidacy, will define the nation's progress, bridging divides and promoting policies that address the collective needs of the population. A strong, inclusive democracy that prioritizes development over division is within reach, driven by a generation ready to lead India into a prosperous future.

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DEMOCRATIC PRINCIPLES IN EDUCATION: THE ROLE OF INDIAN ACADEMIC INSTITUTIONS IN TEACHING AND FOSTERING DEMOCRATIC ENVIRONMENT FOR HARMONIOUS INTERACTIONS

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Abstract

The rising tide of universal interest in educational awareness for democracy has inspired fresh thinking about education for democracy across the globe. Democracy of any country is a structure of government where policies, regulations, management, laws and major activities of a state, national or other polity are directly or indirectly decided by the “individuals” of the society. It is the government, of the people, by the people and for the people. Democratic awareness in education is education which utmost suitably meets the needs of the learning student and on the whole community. It does this through evolving thoughtful personalities who are collective in problem solving and inventive broad thinkers. Democratic awareness can be applicable to learners of all ages in any given knowledge environment. A substantial emphasis is positioned on self-governing schools, colleges and learners as that is where a lot of the formal education in our communities takes place. Each individual inhabits their own place in the vault or field of diversity within democratic awareness and education practices.

Introduction

Democratic awareness in education stimulates the learning process with democratic values of the community, like expressive involvement, individual initiative, and equality, impartiality and justice for all. It sees young people as dynamic recipients of knowledge and active co-creators of their own education and in gaining knowledge. They are not just the harvests of an education system, but rather valued participants in a vibrant learning community. Democratic education begins with the premise that everyone is unique, so each of us learns in a different way. By supporting the individual development of each young person within a caring community, democratic education helps young people learn about themselves, engage with the world around them, and become positive and contributing members of society. Guided by this vision, democratic awareness in education can take numerous forms, each shaped by the by educators, young minds, scholastic programs and societies. Educational institutes executing democratic education by involving practices like self-directed learning, shared decision-making, individualized project-based work, and student-chosen internships in the community. This includes institutions that use the label “democratic institutes “and others that practices these standards and use other terms. Educators productively indulge learners working within the conservative framework of the school, but still need to provide students’ opportunity to have a high-quality in their learning. These teachers go beyond conservative building program to shape more pertinent and engaging experiences that is associated with the lives of young minds.

Democratic Education

Democratic education is an approachable bridge between all institutions in a society with one point objective, to help young people to be creative, responsible citizens, to realize their knowledgeable potential, while at the same time to support the development of the nation

The Institute for Democratic Education in America (IDEA) describes democratic education as “learning that equips every individual to contribute fully in a healthy democracy. It's very significant to note that while democracy is taught in schools, students are not given an occasion to genuinely practice

democracy. Therefore, the question arises: "If we don't practice democracy in our schools, how could we ever expect to end up with democracy in the 'real' world?" (Graves, 2011).

According to Bill Ayers, a democratic education is something based in the culture of democracy and based on some fundamental propositions. A democratic education begins with the initial belief that every individual is of incalculable value. Democratic education is less about facts and dates, it's much more about opening windows and opening doors, learning from the world, not about the world, learning from nature, not about nature, learning from the questions we can generate, and learning from democracy, not about democracy.

Maria Luz Torre also believes that one education to be a democratic it must be a holistic education, not proscriptive, and not limited to the four walls of the classroom. It must be developed emotionally and socially appropriate and it must be participatory. It helps a learner develop a love for learning and critical thinking. It must also be impartial so that all have access to it.

Significant thoughts for making a democratic environment for learning

Democratic awareness education in the educational institutions inspires a understanding in community that they are valued as people, and that they have a constructive role to play in creating a thoughtful community within the institution. Relationships between individuals and teachers gradually progresses as they work democratically together to create a encouraging environment. Creating a democratic classroom environment means involving students, on a regular basis and in developmentally suitable ways, in shared decision making that increases their responsibility for helping to make the classroom a decent place to be and learn.

A democratic classroom contributes to the character because it provides an ongoing forum where students' thoughts are valued and where any need of the group can be addressed, creates a support structure that calls for the students' best moral selves by strengthening community and holding them responsible to practice respect and responsibility, mobilizes the peer culture on the side of virtue, because students are working with the teacher in a continuing partnership to create the moral culture of the classroom, the chief means of creating a democratic classroom environment is the class meeting, a face-to-face circle meeting emphasizing interactive discussion and problem solving. (Cortland).

The explanations above suggest that some of the significances of democratic practices closely relate to the aims and objectives of co-operation, conflict resolution and other areas of peace education. Democratic education is likely to advance a sense of community amongst a group of students and a partnership between teachers and learners based on mutual trust in the capability and creative ability of all those involved in a particular learning process. The movement to promote real participatory democracy through the medium of education involves significant procedural values. These include tolerance of diversity, mutual respect between individuals and groups, a respect for evidence in forming opinions, a willingness to be open to the option of changing one's mind in the light of such evidence, the possession of a critical stance towards some information and finally, seeing that all people have equal social and political rights as human beings. This relates very closely to some of the aims for constructing upon the shared views of being human and relating toward one another with tolerance and kindness are, arguably, shared objectives. There cannot be a realistic agenda for democratic education unless there is an emphasis on reason, open-mindedness and a fairness which the practice of 'real' democracy will ensure. (Union) Democratic education includes the peace education which is focused on fostering an ability to strive for peace in relationships between individuals and groups, establishing a sense of responsibility for one's decisions and actions, developing an understanding of the interdependency of people. These aims predicate particular skills and attitudes like fostering of acquired

skills such as analysis, evaluation and critical thinking, co-operative skills, compassion, clear communication and conflict resolution.

Active Participation of Students in Creating Awareness of a Democratic Environment

Understanding about democracy in academic institutions is very imperative for the survival of our constitutional democracy. Educationalists are challenged to seek and implement means to improve democracy in elementary school. (Hoge, 1996). In order to be able to enthusiastically participate in the environment in which they live and learn, it is necessary to familiarize the students with the basic concepts of democracy, Accountability, Authority, Confidentiality and Justice. The prospectus course contents about responsibility are an overview to the concept that helps students to understand the significance of responsibility in everyday life. They learn to define the responsibility, to identify examples of it, to know the common sources of responsibility and to know what they get to fulfil, and the failures of responsibilities (rewards and punishments). Students are trained to identify the benefits and cost of the fulfilment or non-fulfilment of responsibilities in certain situations, to analyse situations to take responsibility, to evaluate, take and defend its position when it comes to taking some responsibility.

The course content from the concept authority teaches the students the notion of authority and power. They learn to distinguish situations in which people behave in some way on its own initiative and situations in which people behave in some way because someone told them to behave and thus control or guide their actions. Because students are facing daily with multiple rules in the home, in school, in the game etc. they need to learn who creates them, whether they are good rules and if there is a need to create new ones. This content teaches students what is useful to know when it comes to assessing the rules and decide whether they are good rules. Students need to know how to identify deficiencies of rules, to explain the characteristics of a good rule and create a good rule.

Intellectual tools help students to think clearly about issues of these concepts, developing their own position and supporting them with reasons. The knowledge skills they gain are not only in addressing issues of public policy, but also in everyday situations they face in their private life. By thinking for themselves, reaching their own conclusions and defending their position, they can be more effective and active citizen in a free society.

Key Elements of Democratic Education

There are some essential elements of a respectable education for democracy? And why should these elements be at the core of the curriculum in academics? As these elements are necessary qualities of a good education for democracy.

- ✚ Firm foundations in a values culture of equality and shared responsibility. Respect breeds respect. Trust breeds trust. Empathy breeds empathy. Tolerance breeds tolerance. Listening breeds listening.
- ✚ Another essential element of a good education for democracy is teaching and learning knowledge of the Constitution and institutions of the democratic government and civil society in which the students live. A good education for democracy in any country necessarily includes systematic instruction about the principles of the Constitution, the institutions of government under this Constitution, and the nongovernmental institutions that constitute the civil society.
- ✚ Essential element in a good education for democracy is development of the student's tendency and capacity to apply or use knowledge to think and participate competently in a democracy. Basic knowledge of democracy, its principles, practices, and history, ought to be applied by individuals to the civic and political events of the past and present, if so, this knowledge can be

learned thoroughly and used constructively in their lives. So, students need to learn skills of cognition and skills of participation in concert with their acquisition of knowledge.

Participation skills, used in concert with cognitive skills, enable individuals to cooperate with others to monitor and influence the actions and decisions of their government and to make their representatives in government accountable to them. Cognitive skills enable individuals to identify, describe, organize, interpret, explain, and evaluate information and ideas in order to make sense of their experiences and to make decisions about them. If students develop cognitive skills, they can respond to their experiences reasonably and effectively, and when confronted by a public issue, for example, they can make and defend decisions about the matter, as a good citizen should do.

- ✚ Collective decision-making where all members of the community, regardless of age or status, have an equal say over significant decisions such as academic rules, curricula, projects, the hiring of staff and even budgetary matters.
- ✚ Self-directed discovery, Learners choose what they learn, when, how and with whom they learn it. Learning can happen inside or outside of the classroom, through play as well as conventional study. The key is that the learning is following the student's intrinsic motivation and pursuing their interests.
- ✚ Another important essential element of a good education for democracy is participation of students in extracurricular activities that can be connected to the formal teaching and learning experiences required by the curriculum and conducted by teachers in the classrooms of schools. There is a strong relationship between participation in student organizations and team sports and achievement of democratic skills and dispositions. In particular, participation in student government activities can provide opportunities for learning democracy by doing it. Desirable outcomes are maximized, however, when there are strong connections between learning experiences within the curriculum and those in extracurricular activities.
- ✚ Good education for democracy is the teacher-led discussion of current events and issues in an open classroom in which the environment is conducive to and supportive of a free exchange of information and ideas, and where there is mutual tolerance for diverse opinions.

India's embroidery of cultures, traditions, and religions is reflected in its classrooms. Academic institutes are platforms where students learn to navigate and cherish this diversity. By celebrating different festivals, recognizing various historical figures, and encouraging dialogue on diverse issues, these institutions foster a sense of unity in diversity, a cornerstone of democratic ethos. A democratic classroom is one where every student feels heard and valued. Teachers in India are increasingly trained to facilitate equitable participation, recognizing and nurturing the potential of each student irrespective of their background.

Democracy in academic life is more than just a subject; it's a philosophy that Indian academics are earnestly weaving into the educational fabric. By educating young minds about democratic principles, fostering an environment of equality and equity, and serving as models for societal harmony, education in India is playing a crucial role in strengthening the pillars of democracy. It's a slow but steady process of shaping not just informed citizens but engaged ones who value diversity, practice tolerance, and contribute to social unity.

Conclusion

Education for democracy should be brought substantially into university-based programs of teacher education. It is reasonable to presume that if desirable civic education reforms in primary and

secondary schools would succeed, then teachers must be well-prepared to teach democracy and democratic citizenship. Awareness of democratic education inculcates the preparation of students for civic and political life in any country undergoing involvement of democracy. And these above very much essential elements are necessary to the maintenance of democracy in any country that has it and wants to keep it. Through a good educational awareness for democracy in education, our students will learn that the future success of their government and civil society depends eventually on citizens, persons who are just like them. However, without basic knowledge of democracy, skills of cognition and participation in democracy, and civic virtues and dispositions that buttress democracy, citizens cannot sustain and improve their democracy. Indeed, without essential knowledge, skills and virtues, individuals are citizens in name only, because they lack the capacity and power to make good decisions, to carry out their decisions, and to influence their government, as citizens in a democracy are expected to do. Let us, then, resolve to do what it takes to provide our students with a good education for democracy, which is based on the essential elements. And a fundamental part of this long-term goal is to educate and create awareness for democracy in all educational institutions.

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CULTURAL DIVERSITY AND NATIONAL UNITY IN INDIA: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract

In India, in addition to its diverse languages and ethnicities, is recognized for its religious and cultural tolerance. With that said, this paper seeks to outline the relationship between cultural diversity and national integration in India, such as how the nation has been able to incorporate its many different identities over the course of its history, and how modern issues such as political fragmentation and regionalism affect unity. It does this by examining particular cultural and legal institutions such as secularism and federalism in order to demonstrate how strategies are deployed to encourage unity without compromising diversity. Wrapping up with a discussion of how these policies necessarily contribute to inclusiveness, this study argues that India's vulnerabilities can be turned into opportunities if the nation gains, and nurtures, a collective sense of identity that respects the differences in people in the country.

Introduction

Commonly, India is popularly regarded as a “unity in diversity” nation, as they manage to contain an almost unimaginable mix set of languages, religions, ethnicities or traditions under one single Bengal national framework. To be sure, with 22 official languages, 2 dozen deities, not to talk of thousands of tribes, India is the arguably the most hyper-diversified nation. This envisioned India yet presents a singular, today the only, path created around its plural evolution. But formulating and preserving national identity while upholding cultural diversity is a complex task and calls for finding policies that allow the understanding, and indeed celebration, of diversity while maintaining a strong sense of being one nation. This paper, therefore, looks into India's philosophy towards the integration of diversity and the challenges that it poses as well as the policies that have been used to retain unity in the practice of this diverse society.

Historical Perspectives on Cultural Diversity and Unity in India

The idea of cultural unity amidst a national identity is also not a novel idea in India; it is as old as the civilization itself and the evolution of pluralistic thought or philosophy. Even in history, India has been mired with ideologies, thoughts and more aspects traditionally diverse. The Maurya, Gupta and Mughal Empire has fostered and written a culture that allows so many different religions, languages and people to coexist. For instance, Emperor Ashoka's promotion of Buddhism alongside respect for other faiths or Akbar's policy of religious tolerance demonstrated an early understanding of inclusivity.

Furthering such sentiment is the independence movement of Mahatma Gandhi which supplied another perspective. The India that was envisioned to be independent by Gandhi was one that would incorporate myriad faiths, numerous castes and languages, all contributing to a common existence tethered to freedom instead of homogeneity. Such a vision was realized in the Indian Constitution of 1950 in which the Author and the people of India enshrined the freedom of religion, language, and culture in the Constitution's fundamental provisions which institutionalized this principle in the context of a unified nation. This constitutional provision for so-called pluralism has served to be critical in forging the bonds of unity and resolve in the midst of adversity.

Legal and Institutional Frameworks for Protecting Diversity

There is a need for a strong legal framework that protects cultural rights and provides the means to all citizens to maintain their identity, that has its Indian tradition as the core identity. The right to freedom of religion, the right to freedom of expression, the right to cultural practices, and other related fundamental rights ensure individuals and communities the right to their cultural practices and everyday life. The Community Rights over Language grant minorities the right to conserve their language, their script, and their culture and affording them the right to own educational institutions for that purpose.

India's federal structure comes handy in managing different diversities existing within the country. The power sharing of the centre and the states provides for regional self rule which enables governance by the states in accordance with their languages, culture and history. Making it a step towards federalism further promotes national unity, as it recognizes 22 languages under the Eighth Schedule of the Constitution, allowing state officials to use and develop local languages for government and education further encouraging linguistic diversity. These constitutional provisions also enhance diversity while building a sense of national belonging within the nation, hence within the framework of political stability accommodating the pluralism of the country.

Another feature of India's diversity management and unity enhancing features is that which is provided for within the Constitution, the secularism. India's secularism differs with other forms of secularism where complete separation of state and religion is advocated, as it embraces all religions equally without any discrimination or favouritism. This type of secularism allows diverse religions to actively engage and participate in national life without conflict if referred to as "positive secularism".

Contemporary Challenges to National Unity in a Diverse Society

Although India has a long history of pluralistic tendencies, the current sociopolitical scenario depicts a troublesome trend towards the fragmentation of unity amidst the cultural diversity of the country. Political disparities have reached alarming levels, with the politicization of identities doing more to divide than to unite communities for a common purpose. Oftentimes, votes are focused through the lenses of religious, castes or regional identity which is detrimental to the social cohesion processes. This particular aspect of polarization puts the cohesive identity of Indians belonging to multiple backgrounds in jeopardy.

Another problem is that of sub nationalism or regionalism which affects the allegiance of some states or regions which believe that they possess an identity that is significant and sufficient to warrant greater autonomy, recognition or freedom. For instance, the creation of Telangana in 2014 demonstrates the struggle between creating different states and maintaining unity in the borders of one nation, which relates to the subject of overcoming linguistic and cultural distinctions. Federalism definitely provides a way to address these as well, but overzealous sub-nationalism if not contained can rip apart the seams of a cohesive national identity.

Furthermore, exceptionalism driven by religion or caste sometimes tipping into violence also makes it difficult to create a stable society absent of discrimination directed towards the minority regions. Acts of violence targeted towards a particular religion or intolerance of such incidents only serve to erode the relationship communities share with one another and hinder the pluralistic vision of India. These tensions highlight the importance of policies that promote dialogue, empathy, and understanding among diverse groups, reinforcing the idea that national unity depends on inclusive and equitable treatment for all.

Strategies for Strengthening National Unity through Inclusivity

The process of uniting a multi ethnic nation in India demands targeted initiatives which integrate different people's cultural views. Education is important in this regard. By teaching school children the richness of cultures and the oneness of India, mutual appreciation and broader understanding can be inculcated in our young Indians. Cultural education through events like festivals, multi linguistic interactions, and promoting acceptance of others will ensure that the future generation sees diversity as a positive attribute.

The media and other civil society institutions are also crucial in advancing the concept of National integration. Media has been a powerful vehicle to defuse divisive cultural discourses by telling stories of Indian's pluralism and showcasing the works of different communities. Civil society organizations can find many roles in reconciliation between these communities by providing solutions to conflicts that exist and promoting integration. In this regard, interreligious dialogue, cultural exchange, and community participation are all essential in promoting interrelation across cultures.

Policy initiatives that are aimed at enhancing economic inclusion have also been advanced. Social inequalities are often sources of social conflicts, as the underprivileged sectors will tend to understand development in a discriminatory manner. Equitably-focused, education, employment and resource-inclusive economic policies across all communities would narrow socioeconomic divides and promote a common development for the communities. For instance, the construction of new healthcare and educational facilities in rural and tribal areas has a more balanced approach to development since it seeks to combat regional disparities and foster one nation.

Conclusion

India's evolution as a multi-ethnic country attempting to grow into a cohesive state has characteristics that are both peculiar and illuminating. The potential of the country rests in its capacity to celebrate differences as it works towards creating a common identity that encompasses all societies. Furthermore, the legal/institutional context that the Constitution brought and the policies of inclusion and tolerance were all in place for us to be a united country. Nonetheless, other recently emerging problems in the world today, such as political intolerance, regionalism, and ethnic hostility also warrant attention and active intervention and response.

India may continue to uphold the notion of "unity in diversity" by encouraging mutual respect among its citizens, establishing policies that are inclusive, and reinforcing the national dialogue that promotes diversity. The democracy of India and its social cohesiveness depend on the capacity of the nation to harness various voices into a singular national identity. With a clear and inclusive approach, India should be able to deepen its democracy and develop a society in which cultural diversity is an asset, not a disintegration, to posterity's hopes.

FROM COURTROOM TO LAWBOOKS: JUDICIAL INFLUENCE AND LEGISLATIVE ACTION ON GENDER POLICY REFORM IN INDIA

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Abstract

This article examines the comparative effectiveness of judicial advocacy and legislative action in initiating gender policy reform in India. The study focuses on landmark judgments like Vishaka Vs. State of Rajasthan, Joseph Shine Vs. Union of India and NALSA Vs. Union of India. Study uses qualitative analysis of secondary data and highlights the conditions that enable judicial rulings to catalyse policy change. Findings reveal that while judicial rulings can play critical frameworks for advancing gender rights, their impact on public policy is often constrained by other issues like socio-cultural factors and legislative factors. Cases with successful judicial-to-legislative translation demonstrate the importance of public and institutional backing. The cases facing legislative resistance reveal cultural and political challenges. This research suggests that enhanced collaboration between judiciary, legislature, and civil society is essential to bridge the gap between courtroom advocacy and effective policy outcomes.

Key Words: Gender Policy Reform, Judicial Advocacy, Legislative Action, Vishaka Guidelines

Introduction

Gender based inequality is a persistent issue in all our societies. Gender reform through public policy is one of the ways to address gender-based inequalities. In India, in the last few decades judiciary and legislature have played important roles in this direction. Some landmark judgments by the Supreme Court and corresponding legislation have laid the foundation for it. However, the path from the judgement of courts to enactment of specific legislation is often inconsistent. While some judgments have led to a comprehensive act, other progressive rulings of it have not led to similar responses. This inconsistency raises questions about the reasons that cause or hinder the transformation of court judgements into a policy change.

Literature Review

The role of the judicial system in advancing gender equality in India has gained considerable attention of scholars. Jacob's study (2014) examines gender differences in legislative activity in Lok Sabha, lower house of Indian Parliament and finds that female parliamentarians asked fewer questions than their male counterparts. Further the study argues the content of the questions is not different from male legislators and the majority of these questions were not particularly concerned about gender issues. Jha (2014) highlights the landmark judgement by the Supreme Court of India NALSA v. Union of India of 2014. This judgement formally upheld transgender rights under the Indian Constitution. He argues such acts could lead to substantive legislative reforms. Pradeep, M.D (2015) emphasises social justice is essential to ensure women's rights, especially in patriarchal societies. Khan & Arif (2018) examines the Joseph Shine v. Union of India judgement. In this judgement the Supreme Court invalidated Section 497 of the IPC and decriminalised adultery. The study criticises regulation of sexuality by state. It suggests preparing guidelines to balance state intervention in personal matters to promote gender justice.

In Joshi A. D. 's (2019) paper, the contrast between India's reverence for women as symbols of wealth and knowledge and their continued mistreatment has been highlighted. Rashid, et.al. (2020) explores the social-economic and cultural obstacles to gender sensitivity in rural Punjab, Pakistan. The study finds despite some progress women of this region, they face significant barriers. Pooja (2021)

discusses the landmark judgement in Joseph Shine case. She argues adultery is still a moral and societal wrong in India though it has been decriminalised. Kaur's paper (2024) provides an in-depth examination of LGBT rights in India. The study focuses on legislative progress, judicial rulings, and societal attitudes and highlights the challenges faced by these communities.

Research Gap and Objective of the study

There is significant research that has explored both judicial activism and legislative actions in promoting gender rights in India. Still there remains a noticeable gap in systematic studies that directly compare the relative effectiveness of these two institutions in catalysing policy change on gender rights. This lack of a comparative framework leaves an important question underexplored: what factors contribute to the judiciary's success or failure in prompting the legislature to act on gender-related issues? The objective of this study is to assess the conditions that make judicial rulings effective (or ineffective) in prompting policy changes.

Methodology

This study employs a qualitative method. It uses a comparative approach based on secondary data. The comparative design is useful for a systematic exploration of specific cases. The data for this study will be collected from different secondary sources, including case law summaries, full-text court judgments, relevant acts, peer-reviewed articles from journals focusing on gender studies and legislations. The study will analyse and compare cases by their impact on public policy and their socio-political influence. The cases where there is a role of public opinion, media coverage and political will in the policymaking are considered.

Major Cases

The study considers three landmark cases for the comparison. These are the cases where the judiciary has pronounced its judgement on the issue of gender rights but there are differing levels of subsequent legislative action.

First landmark case is *The Vishaka Vs. State of Rajasthan* (1997). This case is a cornerstone example of judicial activism and this case led to effective legislative action. The parliament enacted Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace Act in 2013 based on this judgement. The case was related to the gang rape of a social worker Bhanwari Devi, who attempted to prevent a child marriage. The Supreme Court issued the Vishaka Guidelines under Articles 14, 15, 19, and 21 of the Constitution. These guidelines established preventive measures for workplace sexual harassment. This case is considered as a significant judicial intervention, as it directed all public and private workplaces to adopt guidelines until the parliament passes an act to this effect. The act of 2013 can be attributed to media attention and public advocacy garnered in this case. This case gained substantial media coverage that led to the amplified public demand for a legal framework (Dubey, 2020). Further, political will and institutional support also generated as The Ministry of Women and Child Development pushed for the law in accordance with the Vishaka Guidelines. This institutional support helped to translate judicial directives into formal law. Also, the judicial pressure for Compliance also worked as the Supreme Court specified the guidelines would remain effective until the enactment of new legislation for that purpose.

Second landmark case that this study considers is *Joseph Shine v. Union of India* (2018). In this case the Supreme Court decriminalised adultery and declared that the Section 497 of the IPC violates individual rights. However, despite its significance in reinforcing individual rights, this judgement did not lead to any legislative follow-up. The judgement didn't lead to any amendment to family laws or led to enactment of a law related to marital rights issues. This can be attributed to societal resistance and cultural sensitivity. In India adultery still remains a sensitive topic (Bansal & Pathania, 2024). This

issue has deep-rooted social and cultural implications. Also, there is absence of public and media outrage unlike the Vishaka case. Further, this judgement did not generate sustained public pressure or media demand. This had limited impact on the legislative agenda.

Third important case is NALSA v. Union of India (2014). In this judgement the Supreme Court recognized the rights of transgender individuals as a third gender. The Supreme Court called for affirmative action in education and employment for transgender. Further, the court urged the government to protect the transgender community. It acknowledged the unique challenges faced by the transgender community. This judgement was widely praised for its progressive stance. Parliament enacted the Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act of 2019. This act fell short of the Court's vision. The Act failed to fully protect the rights of transgenders. (Nair & Mishra, 2021). The act has been criticised for neglecting self-identification of these communities, where the Act imposed restrictions not envisioned by Supreme Court judgement. Key factors behind this limited policy impact include inconsistent legislative support. The final Act deviated from several recommendations of the NALSA judgement. There is also a partial public and institutional backing. NALSA's judgement initially received significant praise and later the support from both public and institutional sectors reduced over time.

Findings

Above case comparison reveals several key insights. From this the conditions that facilitate or impede the translation of judicial pronouncements into policy can be deduced. Firstly, public and media advocacy is an important condition. Success of cases like the Vishaka guidelines, indicate that strong public support and sustained media attention act as catalysts for legislative action following progressive court judgements. In contrast, cases lacking public pressure, such as Joseph Shine and NALSA, have not translated into a progressive legislation.

Secondly, political and institutional support is another condition for legislative action. Legislative alignment with judicial rulings is more likely to happen when there is commitment from the political class with support from relevant government institutions. The absence of such support, limits the effectiveness of judicial influence on policy. Finally, social and cultural compatibility also plays a major role. How the society receives the judicial rulings is crucial. Judgments that align with or gain acceptance within the prevailing socio-cultural context are more likely to inspire policy changes. The judgments that challenge deeply ingrained social norms face greater resistance.

Discussion

Above findings reveal structural and social factors that affect the judiciary's ability to drive effective gender policy reforms in India. Court judgments lead to gender policy change only when public support, NGO advocacy, and media visibility align to create socio-political pressure. In Vishaka case, these factors collectively pushed for the comprehensive act-Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace Act in 2013. This highlights the role of the judiciary in setting the way for a gender justice framework. When the judgements resonate with public sentiment and are championed by NGOs and media, they would shape into a decisive policy.

In contrast, some judicial pronouncements on gender issues like decriminalising adultery as in the case of Joseph Shine and addressing transgender rights as in the case of NALSA, face cultural resistance or political hesitation which limits the decisive legislative action. Despite progressive intent these cases encountered reluctance from the parliament. In the NALSA case there is a gap between the Court's broad vision for transgender rights and the resultant act Transgender Persons (Protection of

Rights) Act of 2019 which is narrower. This demonstrates how limited public and political support can dilute judicial influence.

Further, the complex relationship between the judiciary and legislature also reflects inherent limitations in judiciary led reforms. While the judiciary can establish progressive standards, it cannot enforce policy without legislative and executive cooperation. Joseph Shine and NALSA cases reveal this. The judicial influence on policy is constrained by the judiciary's dependence on legislative action. The Vishaka Guidelines case demonstrates how judicial influence is more sustainable when there is legislative support. This illustrates the need for stronger collaboration between these two organs of the government.

Conclusion

Present study has explored the comparative effectiveness of judicial pronouncements and legislative actions in advancing gender policy reform in India. Findings indicate that judicial influence is effective only when there is public support, media attention, and political commitment for the cause. In contrast, even the progressive ruling faced legislative inaction or half-hearted efforts due to cultural resistance and limited political will. Further studies could explore the role of civil society in translating judicial pronouncements into policy in other areas of social justice like LGBTQ+ rights.

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LINKAGES BETWEEN STATE & CENTRAL GOVERNMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA - A STUDY

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Abstract

The connection among state and central governments in the realm of higher education in India is complex and multifaceted, characterized by both collaboration and contention. This paper explores the linkages between the two tiers of governance in shaping higher education policy, funding, and institutional frameworks. With India being a federal structure, the Constitution delineates educational responsibilities, allowing states to govern higher education while the central government provides overarching guidelines, funding, and support for national initiatives.

However, discrepancies in policy implementation, funding allocation, and regulatory frameworks often lead to tensions. This study highlights how these linkages influence the quality, equity, and diversity of higher education institutions across the country.

Furthermore, the paper examines contemporary challenges such as the socio-economic disparities across states, varying degrees of political will, and the impact of globalization on higher education governance. By analysing paper aims to provide insights into effective strategies for enhancing collaboration between state and central governments, thereby supporting a more cohesive and healthy higher education system in India.

Key Words: *Centre-State Relations , Linkages , Higher Education, SWOT Analysis etc.*

• Introduction

The relationship between different tiers of governance is critical in shaping higher education policy, funding, and institutional frameworks. The two tiers of governance typically refer to national (or federal) and subnational (or state/provincial) levels. Here are some key linkages between these two tiers:

1. Policy Formulation

Top-Down Influence: National governments often set broad educational policies and frameworks that guide the overall direction of higher education. This includes legislation related to accreditation, quality assurance, and educational standards.

Bottom-Up Feedback: Subnational governments and institutions can provide feedback based on local needs and circumstances. Their input can shape national policies to be more relevant and applicable to diverse contexts.

2. Funding Mechanisms

Allocation of Resources: National governments usually allocate funding to higher education institutions through grants and subsidies. However, subnational governments often play a key role in distributing these funds, determining which institutions receive support, and what projects are prioritized.

Financial Aid Programs: National policies on student financial assistance can impact state-level funding programs. Subnational governments may design their financial aid systems in alignment with national initiatives to improve accessibility and affordability.

3. Institutional Frameworks

Regulatory Oversight: National policies often establish baseline regulatory frameworks for higher education institutions, including accreditation standards, degree requirements, and institutional governance. Subnational governments may further tailor these regulations to meet local contexts.

Institutional Autonomy: Subnational governments often advocate for greater institutional autonomy, influencing how institutions operate and respond to both national standards and local needs. This dynamic can affect governance structures and decision-making processes within institutions.

4. Collaboration and Partnerships

Intergovernmental Collaboration: National and subnational levels frequently collaborate on higher education initiatives, like research funding, workforce development, and innovation programs. These collaborative efforts enhance the connection between policy objectives and local implementation.

Public-Private Partnerships: Both tiers may engage with industry stakeholders to promote skill development and research initiatives. National policies that encourage such partnerships can lead to local programs that address specific regional economic needs.

5. Accountability and Evaluation

Performance Metrics: National governments may establish performance metrics for higher education institutions, while subnational governments can adapt these metrics to better reflect local priorities, contributing to a more nuanced evaluation of institutional performance.

Data Sharing: Effective linkages require robust data-sharing mechanisms between levels of government. By sharing data, both tiers can make informed decisions on policy changes, funding allocations, and institutional assessments.

6. Capacity Building

Institutional Support Programs: National initiatives aimed at strengthening institutional capacity often require local implementation. This collaboration can enhance the capabilities of higher education bodies to react to both national goals as well as regional needs.

Professional Development: Both layers of governance may work together to provide training and professional development for higher education administrators, ensuring that leadership aligns with both national standards and local-level requirements.

The interplay between national and subnational tiers of governance plays a crucial role in shaping higher education policy, funding, and institutional frameworks. An integrated method that recognizes the strengths and assistances of each level can lead to a more effective and responsive higher education system. Strengthening these linkages fosters collaboration, alignment, and innovation, ultimately enhancing the quality and accessibility of higher education.

• SWOT Analysis Of Linkages Between State And Central Government In Higher Education In India

A SWOT analysis is a tactical instrument recycled to identify and evaluate the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats related to a particular context. Here, we will conduct a SWOT analysis on the linkages between state and central government in the context of higher education in India.

Strengths:

1. **Policy Integration:** The central and state governments can create synergistic policies that cater to regional and national educational needs, improving the overall quality of education.
2. **Resource Sharing:** Collaboration allows for pooling of resources, including funding, infrastructure, and expertise, to enhance academic programs and research.

3. **Diverse Educational Offerings:** The linkages enable a wider variety of courses and programs by integrating curricula and leveraging regional strengths.
4. **Standardization of Education:** Central policies can help standardize educational outcomes and quality across states, contributing to national cohesion in higher education.

Weaknesses:

1. **Bureaucratic Challenges:** Coordination between state and central governments can be hampered by bureaucratic inefficiencies, resulting in delays and miscommunication.
2. **Inconsistencies in Implementation:** Differences in state capacities and priorities may result in inconsistent implementation of central policies, leading to disparities in educational quality.
3. **Political Interference:** Frequent political changes at both levels can lead to instability and inconsistency in educational policy and funding.
4. **Limited Autonomy for Institutions:** Higher education institutions may face restrictions in autonomy, limiting innovation and responsiveness to local needs.

Opportunities:

1. **Increased Investment:** Collaborative initiatives can attract funding from both state and central governments, international organizations, and private investors.
2. **Technological Advancements:** Leveraging technology can enhance collaboration, improve administrative efficiency, and facilitate online learning.
3. **Skill Development Initiatives:** A stronger partnership can promote skill development programs aligned with local and national economic needs, enhancing employability.
4. **Global Collaborations:** Cooperation between state and central governments can create opportunities for international collaborations, exchange programs, and partnerships with foreign institutions.

Threats:

1. **Regional Disparities:** Inequitable resource allocation and attention can exacerbate regional disparities in access to quality higher education in India.
2. **Resistance to Change:** Institutional inertia and resistance from faculty and administrators may hinder collaborative efforts to reform higher education.
3. **Policy Fluctuations:** Changes in political leadership at either level can result in policy reversals, adversely affecting long-term planning and stability in higher education.
4. **Economic Constraints:** Economic downturns can lead to reduced budget allocations for higher education from both central and state governments, affecting institutional sustainability.

The interplay between state and central governments in India's higher education system presents both opportunities and challenges. While there are strengths that can facilitate significant advancements in educational quality and accessibility, weaknesses and threats need to be addressed for effective collaboration. A focus on building strong linkages, enhancing policy coherence, and ensuring equitable resource distribution will be essential for fostering a robust higher education ecosystem in India.

• Challenges Of Linkages Between State And Central Government In Higher Education In India

The linkages between state and central governments in higher education in India present both opportunities and challenges. As both levels of government have roles to play in the management, funding, and regulation of higher educational institutions, several challenges arise, impacting the effectiveness of the educational system.

Here are some key challenges faced:

1. Policy Fragmentation

- **Divergent Policies:** Different policies and approaches adopted by state and central governments can lead to fragmentation, with institutions having to navigate a complex regulatory landscape.
- **Lack of Coordination:** Poor coordination between the two levels can result in overlapping mandates and confusion among stakeholders regarding responsibilities.

2. Funding Discrepancies

- **Inconsistent Funding:** The allocation of funds from the central government may not always align with the needs of state institutions, leading to disparities in resource availability.
- **Dependence on Central Schemes:** State governments are sometimes overly reliant on central schemes for funding, which may not adequately address local needs.

3. Quality and Accreditation Issues

- **Variable Standards:** Differing quality standards set by state and central authorities can lead to inconsistencies in the quality of education across the country.
- **Accreditation Challenges:** Institutions may face difficulties in meeting accreditation requirements that are imposed by multiple regulatory bodies from both the state and central levels.

4. Regulatory Burdens

- **Overlapping Regulations:** Institutions may be subject to multiple regulations from both state and central authorities, leading to bureaucratic hurdles and inefficiencies.
- **Compliance Complexity:** Navigating the compliance requirements of both governments can be cumbersome for institutions, diverting resources away from educational outcomes.

5. Political Interference

- **Politicization of Education:** Political factors often influence decision-making in higher education, leading to challenges in implementing policies effectively and promoting meritocracy.
- **Regional Bias:** Political considerations may lead to favoritism towards certain regions, impacting equitable access to education across states.

6. Human Resource Challenges

- **Staff Shortages:** Disparities in staffing and faculty development initiatives between states may impact the quality of education provided.
- **Training and Development:** Variability in professional development opportunities for faculty and staff can hinder institutional growth and effectiveness.

7. Technology Integration

- **Digital Divide:** Differences in digital infrastructure and access between states can impair the effective implementation of technology-driven educational initiatives.
- **Competition for Resources:** Competition between state governments for central funds for digital initiatives can divert focus from local educational needs.

8. Student Mobility and Access

- **Barriers to Access:** Students from certain regions may face challenges related to access and mobility due to differing state policies and regulations.
- **Inconsistent Admission Policies:** Variability in admission criteria and processes can complicate the higher education landscape, impacting student choices.

9. Cultural and Linguistic Differences

- **Regional Languages and Cultures:** The diverse cultural and linguistic landscape of India can complicate the uniform implementation of educational policies.

- **Localization of Curriculum:** Balancing national educational standards with regional context can be a challenge in curriculum design and implementation.

10. Long-term Vision and Strategic Planning

- **Short-term Focus:** A lack of long-term vision in developing higher education frameworks can result in inconsistent policy implementation and vision alignment.
- **Strategic Disparities:** Differences in strategic priorities between state and central governments can hinder collaborative initiatives.

Addressing these challenges requires a committed partnership between state and central governments, with a focus on improving coordination, aligning policies, and fostering a more integrated approach to higher education. Enhanced collaborative frameworks and dialogue between both levels can lead to a more effective higher education system in India, promoting equity, quality, and accessibility.

• Remedial Measures to Overcome Challenges Of Linkages Between State And Central Government In Higher Education In India

Addressing the challenges of linkages between state and central governments in higher education in India requires a multifaceted approach. Here are some remedial measures that can help overcome these challenges:

1. Policy Harmonization

- **Coordinated Policy Frameworks:** Develop joint frameworks that align state and central education policies to ensure consistency in governance and quality standards.
- **Regular Policy Reviews:** Establish periodic reviews to adapt policies to emerging educational needs and challenges, fostering flexibility in both state and central educational policies.

2. Improved Communication

- **Inter-Governmental Committees:** Create regular forums or committees where state and central government officials can meet to discuss higher education issues, share best practices, and coordinate efforts.
- **Feedback Mechanisms:** Institute systems for stakeholders (students, educators, administrators) to provide feedback on policies, improving responsiveness and relevance to local contexts.

3. Resource Allocation

- **Equitable Funding Mechanisms:** Formulate funding strategies that ensure fair allocation of resources to state universities, taking into account regional needs and socio-economic disparities.
- **Performance-Based Grants:** Introduce funding based on institutions' performance metrics to encourage efficiency and accountability.

4. Capacity Building

- **Training Programs:** Develop training initiatives for state officials and university administrators on effective governance, management practices, and policy implementation.
- **Knowledge Sharing Initiatives:** Foster a culture of collaboration by facilitating knowledge exchange between institutions in different states and central agencies.

5. Decentralization of Administration

- **Empower State Governments:** Grant more authority and autonomy to state governments in managing higher education institutions, including faculty recruitment, curriculum design, and admissions processes.
- **Local Governance Models:** Promote local governance models in education that cater to regional needs while aligning with national educational objectives.

6. Enhancing Quality and Standards

- **Standardized Accreditation Processes:** Create unified accreditation standards recognized by both the central and state governments, ensuring all institutions meet quality benchmarks.
- **Collaborative Research Initiatives:** Encourage collaborations between state and central universities for research projects, fostering innovation and enhancing higher education quality.

7. Leveraging Technology

- **Integrated Education Management Systems:** Implement digital platforms that facilitate data sharing and management between state and central governments, enhancing transparency and coordination.
- **Online Learning and Resources:** Develop online resources and courses that can be accessed universally, providing equitable access to quality education.

8. Stakeholder Engagement

- **Inclusivity in Decision-Making:** Involve educators, students, and community representatives in policy formulation, ensuring diverse perspectives are considered.
- **Public-Private Partnerships:** Encourage partnerships with private institutions and organizations to foster innovation and provide additional resources for public universities.

9. Monitoring and Evaluation

- **Regular Assessment Reports:** Establish mechanisms for regular assessment of how well central and state policies are aligned and their impact on higher education outcomes.
- **Setting Benchmarks:** Define clear benchmarks for success in collaboration and linkage between state and central government initiatives in higher education.

10. Awareness Campaigns

- **Public Awareness Drives:** Conduct campaigns to educate citizens about higher education policies, funding opportunities, and available resources, fostering greater engagement and accountability.

By implementing these remedial measures, India can enhance the effectiveness of linkages between state and central governments in higher education, leading to improved educational outcomes and empowering a diverse student population across the nation.

Concluded Observations:

The linkages between state and central government in higher education in India are multifaceted and deeply rooted in the country's federal structure. Overall, these linkages can be understood through the following conclusions:

1. **Shared Responsibilities:** The higher education system in India is characterized by a dual governance structure where both the central and state governments play significant roles. The Central Government is primarily responsible for national policies, funding, and quality assurance, while the State Governments manage the implementation and administration of these policies at the local level. This necessitates collaboration and coordination to ensure effective functioning.
2. **Policy Formulation and Implementation:** The central government sets broad educational policies and priorities through regulations and frameworks, such as the National Policy on Education (NPE). The state governments, in turn, adapt these policies to local needs and contexts, which can lead to variations in implementation quality and effectiveness across states.
3. **Funding Mechanisms:** Funding for higher education in India comes from both central and state sources. The central government allocates funds through schemes like the Higher Education Funding Agency (HEFA) and provides grants to various universities and colleges. States also have

their own budgetary provisions for higher education. This shared funding responsibility can lead to disparities in resource allocation, affecting the quality and accessibility of education.

4. **Regulatory Frameworks:** The Central Government establishes regulatory bodies like the University Grants Commission (UGC) and the All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE) to oversee higher education standards nationwide. State governments are often responsible for local universities and colleges, which can create tension between central mandates and state-level autonomy.
5. **Decentralization and Autonomy:** While the central government sets overarching goals, there is an increasing push for decentralization and institutional autonomy in higher education. This allows states and individual institutions to innovate and cater to regional demands, but it also raises concerns about maintaining a uniform quality of education.
6. **Challenges in Coordination:** Despite the necessity for collaboration, challenges often arise in communication and coordination between state and central governments. Differences in priorities, bureaucratic hurdles, and political influences can lead to inefficiencies and hindered progress in the higher education sector.
7. **Focus on Inclusivity and Equity:** Both levels of government have expressed commitment to enhancing access to higher education for marginalized communities, yet the effectiveness of these initiatives varies. Collaborative efforts are required to ensure that policies translate into tangible improvements in inclusivity and equity across the country.
8. **Impact of Technological Advancements:** The rise of technology in education has prompted both central and state governments to embrace new methods of teaching and learning. This presents opportunities for synergy, but also challenges in terms of infrastructure, training, and equal access.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the linkages between the state and central government in higher education in India are complex and crucial for the development of a robust educational framework. Effective collaboration, clear communication, and a commitment to shared goals are essential for overcoming challenges and ensuring that higher education contributes positively to the socio-economic advancement of the country.

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REGIONAL DISPARITIES: UNDERSTANDING THE UNEQUAL GEOGRAPHIES OF DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Regional disparities, often characterized by substantial variations in economic, social, and infrastructural development across different geographical areas, have been a persistent challenge for policymakers, researchers, and society at large. Regional disparities manifest in various forms, encompassing differences in income levels, educational attainment, healthcare access, employment opportunities, and overall quality of life. The disparities are shaped by a complex interplay of historical, geographical, political, and economic factors. The causes of regional disparities are diverse and interconnected ranging from Historical legacies to geographical factors including natural resources, climate, and proximity to transportation hubs, which can also influence regional development patterns. Furthermore, policy decisions, investment allocation, and governance structures can exacerbate or mitigate disparities.

Addressing regional disparities requires a comprehensive approach that integrates short-term and long-term strategies. Policymakers must consider targeted interventions, such as infrastructure development, education and healthcare access, and job creation initiatives, in regions with the greatest disparities. Moreover, fostering regional collaboration and decentralization of decision-making can empower local communities to take ownership of their development trajectories. This abstract underscores the significance of research and data-driven analysis in understanding regional disparities. As technology and globalization continue to reshape the world, the dynamics of regional disparities evolve, demanding adaptive strategies. By addressing the root causes and consequences of regional disparities, societies can work towards a more equitable and sustainable future, where every region has the opportunity to thrive.

Key Words: Regional Disparities, communities, globalization, decision-making

Introduction

In an increasingly interconnected and globalized world, the dynamics of development are not uniform. Instead, they vary significantly from one region to another, creating what is often referred to as "regional disparities." These disparities manifest as differences in economic prosperity, social well-being, infrastructure, education, and overall quality of life between different geographical connects. Understanding and addressing unequal geographies of development is a critical challenge for policymakers, researchers, and communities worldwide.

This introductory exploration seeks to shed light on the multifaceted nature of regional disparities, delving into the root causes, consequences, and potential solutions to address this complex issue. It also aims to explore how the disparities affect individuals, communities, and nations, and the broader implications for global stability and development. Furthermore, this discussion will emphasize that regional disparities are not solely economic but intertwined with disparities in healthcare access, educational opportunities, infrastructure development, and environmental conditions. Addressing regional disparities requires a holistic approach that considers both economic and non-economic

dimensions. Additionally, this exploration will underline that regional disparities are not limited to developing countries. This paper attempts to state and understand that regional disparities are universal, transcending geographical and developmental boundaries.

To make strides in reducing regional disparities, it is essential to comprehend the driving forces behind them such as historical legacies, geographical features, policy decisions, and market forces. This exploration aims to understand the dynamics and formulate effective strategies to narrow the gaps. Finally, initiate critical discussions and resultant action in mitigating regional disparities.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of studying regional disparities is multifaceted and includes the following key objectives:

1. **Identifying Inequities:** One of the primary purposes is to identify and analyze disparities in income, wealth, employment opportunities, infrastructure, education, and healthcare, among different regions to identify areas that are lagging in terms of development.
2. **Understanding the Causes:** Aim to understand the underlying causes of regional disparities and factors contributing to disparities. By comprehending these causes, policymakers can develop targeted strategies for reducing disparities.
3. **Policy Formulation:** Regional disparities studies provide insights for policymakers to formulate policies and interventions to promote balanced regional development. This involves investments in infrastructure, education, healthcare, and support for industries.
4. **Economic Efficiency:** Regional disparities not only affect social equity but also economies. Balancing development across regions can lead to better overall economic efficiency by harnessing the full potential of a country's or a region's resources and talents.
5. **Social Cohesion:** Reducing disparities can effectively reduce social tensions. Huge disparities between regions can lead to social unrest and migration from underdeveloped to developed areas, putting pressure on urban centers and exacerbating inequalities.
6. **Sustainable Development:** Regional development studies also consider environmental sustainability. Balanced development can reduce environmental degradation in heavily developed areas and encourage sustainable practices in less developed regions.
7. **Measuring Progress:** Regional development indicators are often used as measures of progress and success in achieving development goals. Monitoring and assessing disparities over time can help gauge the effectiveness of policies and interventions.
8. **Global Perspective:** Understanding regional disparities is crucial in the context of globalization. It helps nations and regions position themselves in the global economy, identify competitive advantages, and adapt to changing global economic trends.
9. **Academic Inquiry:** From an academic perspective, the study of regional disparities contributes to an understanding of economics, sociology, geography, and public policy. Scholars explore the complex interactions between factors influencing development.

The study of regional disparities serves both social and economic purposes. It seeks to reduce inequalities, enhance economic efficiency, promote social cohesion, and contribute to sustainable development.

Reasons for Regional Disparities in India

Regional disparities in India are a complex issue with multiple factors contributing to the disparities in economic development, infrastructure, education, and healthcare among different regions of the country. Here are some of the key reasons for regional disparities in India:

1. Historical Factors:

The British colonial rule had a significant impact on the economic and social structure of India, concentrating resources and development in certain regions. The presence of princely states led to variations in governance, taxation, and development across regions.

2. Economic Factors:

Regions that experienced early industrialization and investment had a head start in economic development in comparison to the backward areas. Unequal infrastructure development, including transportation, energy, and communication networks, affects regional economic growth.

3. Educational Disparities:

Better educational infrastructure and access to quality schools and universities create a skilled workforce and higher human capital. Disparities in literacy rates exist, with some states and regions having higher literacy rates than others.

4. Healthcare Disparities:

Access to healthcare facilities, including hospitals and clinics, varies widely across regions. Disparities in health outcomes, with some regions experiencing higher morbidity and mortality rates due to a lack of healthcare access and awareness.

5. Political Factors:

State governments play a significant role in regional development through policies related to taxation, subsidies, and infrastructure investment. Corruption and inefficiency in governance can hinder development in some regions more than others.

6. Geographical Factors:

Geography, climate, and the availability of natural resources can significantly impact regional development opportunities. Regions prone to natural disasters may experience setbacks in development due to recurring damage and reconstruction needs.

7. Population Density:

The high population density in some regions can strain resources and infrastructure, making it challenging to provide services and opportunities for all.

8. Migration Patterns:

Migration from rural to urban areas can lead to a concentration of economic activity in certain cities, exacerbating regional disparities. Seasonal labor migration from poorer regions to more prosperous ones can contribute to disparities in income.

9. Socio-cultural Factors:

The caste system and social hierarchies continue to influence economic opportunities and social mobility in certain regions. Cultural practices and traditions may impact education, healthcare, and economic development.

Addressing regional disparities in India requires a multi-faceted approach, including targeted policies, investments in infrastructure and education, and efforts to promote equitable economic growth and development across all regions of the country.

Case Study of Regional Disparities in India

BIMARU states

Regional disparities in India, particularly in the BIMARU states (Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, and Uttar Pradesh), have been a significant challenge. These states have historically lagged in economic growth, human development indicators, and infrastructure development.

A closer look reveals regional disparities in these states:

The term "BIMARU" was coined in the 1980s to describe the poor socio-economic conditions of the four northern Indian states. Since then, there have been efforts by both the central and state governments to address these disparities, but progress has been slow and uneven.

Economic Disparities:

BIMARU states consistently have lower per capita income compared to other states in India. Bihar and Uttar Pradesh have been particularly affected by this disparity. These states rely heavily on agriculture, which is often characterized by low productivity, outdated farming techniques, and a lack of diversification. This makes them vulnerable to weather-related shocks. These states' industrial and manufacturing sectors have not seen significant growth compared to other regions, leading to a lack of job opportunities and economic diversification.

Social and Human Development Disparities:

BIMARU states have historically had lower literacy rates and poor school infrastructure. While there have been improvements in recent years, they still lag in quality education. Access to quality healthcare services in these states is limited, resulting in higher maternal and child mortality rates. Malnutrition and sanitation-related issues are prevalent. BIMARU states have high population growth rates, which adds additional pressure on resources and services hindering economic and social development efforts.

Infrastructure Disparities:

The road infrastructure in these states, especially in rural areas, is inadequate, hampering connectivity and economic development. Access to reliable electricity and clean drinking water remains a challenge in many parts affecting the quality of life and economic activities.

The central and state governments have launched several initiatives to address these disparities, such as the Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY) for rural road connectivity, the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) for universal elementary education, and various healthcare programs.

Challenges

Political Factors: Political instability, corruption, and governance issues have at times hindered the effective implementation of development programs in these states.

Social Factors: Issues like caste-based discrimination and social inequalities have deep-rooted effects on development efforts.

Resource Constraints: Limited financial resources and administrative capacity can impede development initiatives in these states.

Thus, BIMARU states of India highlights the complex challenges that arise from historical and structural factors. Despite efforts, significant disparities persist. Addressing disparities requires sustained efforts in sectors like education, healthcare, infrastructure, and economic diversification. It's a long-term endeavor that necessitates collaboration between the central and state governments, as well as the involvement of civil society to bring about balanced regional development.

The North Eastern States of India

Regional disparities in the North Eastern states of India are characterized by variations in economic development, infrastructure, social indicators, and access to basic services. This case study will provide an overview of these disparities and some potential factors contributing to them. The North Eastern states of India consist of eight states: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, and Tripura. These states are characterized by their hilly terrain, remote locations, diverse ethnic groups, and unique cultures.

Economic Disparities:

Income levels in the North Eastern states are generally lower than the national average. States like Assam and Tripura have relatively higher per capita income compared to other North Eastern states, while states like Nagaland and Manipur have lower income levels. The lack of large-scale industries and scarce private-sector investments have hindered industrialization. Apart from Assam's tea and oil industries, most states face challenges in attracting investments.

Infrastructure Disparities:

Inadequate road and rail connectivity in hilly terrain makes transportation difficult. It affects trade, tourism, and the economy. The region is heavily reliant on road transport, leading to delays and high transportation costs. Many areas in the North Eastern states lack reliable access to electricity. This lack of energy infrastructure inhibits industrialization and affects the quality of life.

Social Disparities:

The literacy rate in some states, such as Nagaland and Manipur, remains below the national average. Lack of access to quality education and language barriers perpetuate disparity. Healthcare infrastructure is underdeveloped, leading to disparities in healthcare access. Remote regions often lack proper medical facilities, and healthcare indicators are below the national average.

Factors Contributing to Disparities

The region's geographical isolation from the rest of India has hindered economic integration and trade. Landlocked states like Manipur and Mizoram face additional challenges. Ongoing insurgency movements in some states, such as Nagaland and Manipur, have deterred investment and development efforts. Inter-ethnic tensions can impede development efforts. Historical underinvestment in infrastructure, especially in transportation and energy, has hindered economic growth. Challenges in policy implementation, including issues related to governance, corruption, and bureaucracy, can exacerbate regional disparities.

Efforts to Address Disparities

Some states, like Assam and Manipur, have been granted Special Category Status, entailing financial incentives and assistance from the central government to promote development. Efforts have been made to attract investments in sectors like tourism, horticulture, and handicrafts, leveraging the region's unique cultural and natural assets. The central government has initiated projects to improve road connectivity, expand airports, and enhance digital infrastructure. Ongoing peace talks with insurgent groups aim to bring stability to the region, which could facilitate development. Skill development programs are being implemented to enhance the employability of the local population.

Recommendation for Addressing Regional Disparities

Addressing regional disparities is an important goal for promoting equitable development and ensuring that all regions have access to opportunities and resources. Here are some recommendations for addressing regional disparities:

Data Collection and Analysis: Collection and analysis of data on regional disparities followed by understanding the economic, social, and infrastructural gaps between regions. This will help in formulating targeted policies.

Infrastructure Investment: Investment in infrastructure development like roads, bridges, public transportation, and digital infrastructure in less-developed regions. This can attract business and stimulate economic growth.

Education and Skill Development: Promote quality education and skills development programs in disadvantaged regions. A skilled workforce can attract industries and create job opportunities.

Regional Specialization: Identification of unique strengths and resources of each region and encourage specialization. Areas with fertile land can focus on agriculture, while regions with skilled labor can promote manufacturing or technology sectors.

Incentives for Businesses: Special incentives for businesses to set up operations in less-developed regions. Tax breaks, grants, and other incentives make it attractive for companies.

Entrepreneurship and Small Businesses: Support entrepreneurship and the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises in disadvantaged regions. These businesses often drive local economies.

Regional Planning and Governance: Improve regional planning and governance structures. The decision-making apparatus must include representation from all affected regions and evaluate the unique challenges and opportunities of each.

Access to Finance: Access to financial services and credit for individuals and businesses in disadvantaged regions. Microfinance programs and community banks can help in this regard.

Healthcare and Social Services: Access to quality healthcare and social services in all regions. Health and well-being are critical for economic and social development.

Promote Tourism and Culture: Develop and promote tourism highlighting the cultural and natural attractions of less-developed regions. Tourism can create jobs and boost the local economy.

Investment in Research and Development: Encourage research and development activities in universities and research institutions located in disadvantaged regions. Innovation can lead to the emergence of new industries.

Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs): Foster partnerships between governments, the private sector, and NGOs to implement development projects in less-developed regions. PPPs can leverage resources and expertise.

Monitoring and Evaluation: Continuous monitoring of the progress aimed at reducing regional disparities. Regular evaluation will help recalibrate policies and strategies as needed.

Community Engagement: Involve local communities in the decision-making process and development initiatives. Their insights, experience, and participation are crucial.

Inclusive Policies: Developing policies that target vulnerable populations within disadvantaged regions, such as marginalized communities and indigenous groups.

Concluding Observations

Regional disparities refer to the unequal distribution of economic, social, and developmental opportunities and outcomes among different geographical regions within a country or across the world. Addressing these disparities requires a multi-faceted approach, including targeted policies that promote inclusive growth, investment in infrastructure, and enhanced educational opportunities. These disparities can have significant implications for individuals, communities, and nations as a whole. Regional Disparities are a persistent challenge that requires concerted efforts at various levels, from local to global, to address. Achieving greater equity in development not only benefits marginalized regions but can also contribute to overall economic growth, social stability, and a more sustainable future for all. Collaborative efforts among government, civil society, and the private sector will be essential to bridge these gaps and create a more balanced and prosperous nation. It is a goal that calls for continued research, policy innovation, and a commitment to addressing the root causes of regional disparities.

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- Bureau of Economic Analysis (BEA) - Look for regional economic data and reports, especially if you're researching disparities in the United States.
- European Commission - The EU publishes reports on regional disparities within its member states.
- Reports from the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), National Institution for Transforming India (NITI Aayog), and Census of India provide valuable data and analysis on regional disparities.

PLURALISM IN MEDIA AND PUBLIC DISCOURSE IN INDIA: A SOCIOLOGICAL INSIGHT INTO DIVERSITY, CHALLENGES, AND DEMOCRATIC VALUES

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Abstract

Pluralism in media and public discourse is critical for fostering democratic values and social harmony in a diverse country like India. This study explores the sociological dimensions of media pluralism, examining its role in representing India's multifaceted identity while addressing challenges such as commercialization, political interference, and technological disruptions. Utilizing secondary research and thematic analysis, the paper identifies gaps in media representation, particularly for marginalized communities, and highlights the implications of digital platforms in amplifying or silencing diverse voices. Strategies for fostering inclusivity, such as policy reforms, media literacy, and support for regional and grassroots media, are also discussed. By addressing these challenges, this paper provides pathways for creating a more equitable and representative media landscape.

Keywords: *Pluralism, Media, Democratic Values, Challenges, Marginalised Communities Sociological Insights*

Introduction

India, as one of the most diverse nations in the world, is home to an unparalleled mosaic of cultures, languages, religions, and ideologies. This diversity makes pluralism—a system that accommodates multiple perspectives and voices—not just a democratic ideal but an essential framework for maintaining societal harmony. In this context, media and public discourse play pivotal roles as facilitators of pluralistic engagement. The media serves as a critical instrument for amplifying voices, shaping public opinion, and fostering informed debates, which are integral to a functioning democracy. Public discourse, mediated through various channels such as print, broadcast, and digital media, reflects the ongoing negotiation of identities, interests, and ideologies within society. It is through these platforms that citizens engage with issues of public importance, challenge power structures, and seek solutions to societal problems. However, in a country as complex as India, ensuring that media and public discourse remain pluralistic and inclusive is a persistent challenge. The socio-political landscape, characterized by deeply entrenched hierarchies of caste, class, gender, and religion, often skews representation, silencing marginalized voices.

The importance of pluralism in media cannot be overstated. A pluralistic media landscape ensures that no single ideology, interest group, or narrative monopolizes the public sphere. Instead, it fosters a vibrant exchange of ideas, creating space for the representation of diverse identities and perspectives. This inclusivity is crucial for upholding the democratic values of equality, justice, and liberty. Yet, media pluralism in India is increasingly under threat from factors such as commercialization, political interference, and technological disruptions. These challenges compromise the media's ability to serve as a truly independent and inclusive platform.

This paper delves into the sociological dimensions of media pluralism and public discourse in India, examining their significance in a democracy and their role in reflecting the country's diversity. It

explores the obstacles that hinder pluralism, such as biased reporting, underrepresentation of marginalized communities, and the rising polarization of narratives. Furthermore, it considers how emerging technologies and digital platforms, while democratizing access to information, also introduce new challenges, such as echo chambers and misinformation.

By analysing the current state of media pluralism and public discourse in India, this study seeks to provide insights into the ways in which these institutions can better embody the principles of inclusivity and diversity. Ultimately, it argues that fostering pluralism in media and public discourse is not merely a matter of ethical journalism but a necessity for sustaining India's democratic and multicultural identity.

Literature Review

Media pluralism and public discourse are integral to the democratic fabric of any society, particularly in a diverse and multicultural country like India. Existing literature sheds light on the various dimensions of media pluralism, the challenges it faces, and its role in fostering inclusive democratic values. This review synthesizes key scholarly contributions to understand the sociological underpinnings of these concepts.

Media Pluralism and Diversity

Karppinen's *Rethinking Media Pluralism* (2013) critically examines traditional concepts of media pluralism and suggests that mere diversity in ownership or content does not guarantee inclusivity. Karppinen advocates for a broader framework that includes equitable representation of voices from marginalized communities. Chaudhuri (2011) extends this discussion to the Indian context in *Refashioning India: Gender, Media, and a Transformed Public Discourse*, where she explores how gender identities are represented and contested in Indian media. She argues that while the media reflects broader social transformations, it often falls short of providing a platform for marginalized voices, particularly women.

Challenges to Media Pluralism

The increasing commercialization of media has significantly impacted its ability to uphold pluralistic ideals. Dwyer (2010) highlights how media convergence has led to the concentration of ownership, reducing the diversity of perspectives available to the public. In India, the dominance of large media conglomerates often marginalizes regional and alternative voices. Rajagopal (2001), in *Politics After Television*, examines how political influences shape media narratives, particularly in the context of Hindu nationalism. His analysis underscores the role of media in both reinforcing and challenging majoritarian ideologies.

Media and Democratic Values

Gans (2003), in *Democracy and the News*, underscores the necessity of a free and diverse press for democratic functioning. He argues that pluralistic media is essential for holding power accountable and fostering informed citizen participation. The role of media in upholding democratic values in India is further explored in "Majoritarianism and the Future of India's Democracy" (2020), which discusses how biased media narratives can either challenge or reinforce authoritarian tendencies in governance.

Representation in Public Discourse

Representation of marginalized communities in public discourse is a recurring theme in the literature. The study *A Partition of Contingency? Public Discourse in Bengal, 1946-1947* (2008) highlights how media narratives during significant historical periods reflect societal divides. Similarly, Chaudhuri (2011) critiques the Indian media's limited coverage of caste-based issues, which often reflects the biases of dominant social groups.

Technological Impacts on Media Pluralism

The digital revolution has transformed media landscapes, introducing both opportunities and challenges for pluralism. Morisi (2018) explores how technological advancements, such as big data and artificial intelligence, influence media diversity. In India, while digital platforms have democratized access to information, they have also facilitated echo chambers and the spread of misinformation, complicating efforts to maintain pluralism.

Policy and Regulation

The role of policy in promoting media pluralism is emphasized in Sundar's (2022) analysis of India's media landscape. He argues that regulatory measures must balance the need for media freedom with interventions to prevent monopolies and ensure fair representation. The critique of India's Broadcasting Bill, as discussed in "India's Broadcasting Bill is an Exercise in State Control" (2022), highlights the tension between state control and media independence, pointing to the need for nuanced policy frameworks.

The reviewed literature underscores the multifaceted nature of media pluralism and its vital role in democratic societies. While the media in India has the potential to reflect the country's diversity, challenges such as commercialization, political interference, and technological disruptions hinder its effectiveness. Addressing these issues requires policy interventions, ethical journalism, and an emphasis on inclusive representation to ensure that the media remains a platform for diverse and equitable public discourse.

Objectives for the Study

1. To assess how media pluralism reflects India's socio-cultural diversity and includes marginalized voices.
2. To analyze the challenges to pluralism in Indian media, focusing on commercialization, political interference, and technological disruptions.
3. To identify strategies for fostering inclusivity and safeguarding democratic values through media pluralism.

Methodology

This study employs a secondary research methodology to explore media pluralism and public discourse in India. It relies on data collected from credible academic sources such as Google Scholar, JSTOR, and institutional reports, focusing on peer-reviewed articles, books, and policy documents. The gathered data is analysed thematically, emphasizing key areas such as diversity in media, challenges to pluralism, representation of marginalized voices, and the influence of digital technologies. Specific case studies, such as the media coverage of social movements and marginalized communities, are examined to illustrate the practical implications of media pluralism. A critical evaluation is conducted to identify gaps and biases in existing media practices and policies, providing a comprehensive understanding of the sociological dimensions of media pluralism in India. This approach highlights the importance of fostering inclusive and equitable media representation in a diverse democratic society.

Pluralism and Its Significance in Media

Pluralism in media refers to the representation of diverse perspectives, cultures, ideologies, and identities, ensuring that media platforms contribute to democratic participation, representation, and conflict resolution. A pluralistic media landscape allows citizens to remain informed and actively participate in decision-making processes (Karppinen, 2013). It provides visibility to marginalized groups often excluded from mainstream narratives, thereby addressing systemic imbalances (Chaudhuri, 2011). Additionally, the presence of diverse viewpoints fosters dialogue and mutual

understanding, aiding in conflict resolution and social cohesion (Gans, 2003). In the Indian context, media platforms, ranging from traditional print and broadcast outlets to digital forums, play a crucial role in representing the country's multilingual, multiethnic, and multicultural population. These platforms act as instruments for amplifying the voices of diverse communities while bridging societal divides (Sundar, 2022).

Public Discourse: A Sociological Perspective

Public discourse in India is deeply influenced by factors such as caste, religion, language, and gender, which shape societal perceptions and policymaking processes. Media often acts as a mediator in these discussions, framing issues in ways that reflect or challenge prevailing power dynamics (Rajagopal, 2001). However, this potential for inclusivity is frequently undermined by polarization, where media narratives amplify political and ideological divides. Caste and religious biases also limit the visibility of marginalized communities, with dominant groups overshadowing their narratives (Chaudhuri, 2011). Similarly, gender imbalances are prevalent, as women and LGBTQ+ individuals remain underrepresented in both media narratives and broader public discussions (Chaudhuri, 2011; Sundar, 2022).

Case Studies: Media and Public Discourse in India

Specific case studies highlight the practical implications of media pluralism and its limitations. For instance, the farmers' protests of 2020–2021 revealed the contrasting roles of mainstream and alternative media. While mainstream outlets often aligned with government narratives, digital platforms provided a space for dissenting voices, demonstrating the importance of diverse media representation (Majoritarianism and the Future of India's Democracy, 2020). Similarly, the coverage of caste-based issues frequently reflects biases, with the atrocities faced by marginalized communities, such as Dalits, often underreported (Chaudhuri, 2011). Gendered narratives in media also reveal persistent stereotypes, as women are often portrayed in roles of victimhood rather than empowerment. However, movements like #MeToo showcased the transformative potential of alternative media in amplifying marginalized voices (Chaudhuri, 2011).

Media Pluralism and Democratic Values

Media pluralism is fundamental to democratic values, fostering accountability, civic engagement, and freedom of expression. A pluralistic media landscape ensures government accountability by exposing corruption and malpractices, with investigative journalism playing a vital role (Gans, 2003). It also promotes civic engagement by raising awareness about social issues and encouraging participatory democracy (Karppinen, 2013). Moreover, pluralism safeguards freedom of expression by providing citizens the opportunity to voice dissent without fear of censorship or persecution, an essential component of a functioning democracy (Sundar, 2022).

Strategies to Enhance Media Pluralism in India

Addressing the challenges to media pluralism requires targeted strategies, including policy interventions, support for regional media, digital inclusion, and promoting diversity. Policy measures should prevent monopolies and encourage public service broadcasting to provide balanced content (Dwyer, 2010). Strengthening regional and grassroots media through financial and infrastructural support is also critical for ensuring the representation of local concerns (Sundar, 2022). Bridging the digital divide by improving internet access and digital literacy, particularly in rural areas, can democratize access to information. Combating misinformation through fact-checking initiatives and media literacy programs is equally essential (Morisi, 2018). Additionally, encouraging the inclusion of marginalized groups in media production and editorial roles, and promoting content that reflects India's

pluralistic identity, are vital steps towards achieving a more inclusive media environment (Chaudhuri, 2011).

Future of Media and Public Discourse in India

The future of media pluralism in India depends on striking a balance between technological advancements and ethical journalism. Emerging technologies like artificial intelligence and big data offer opportunities for personalized and inclusive media but also raise concerns about surveillance and algorithmic biases (Morisi, 2018). Public discourse must adapt to these changes, fostering critical thinking and inclusivity while addressing the challenges posed by polarization and misinformation. By adopting these strategies, media can become a powerful tool for sustaining India's democratic values and ensuring the representation of its diverse population.

Conclusion

Media pluralism and public discourse are cornerstones of a robust democracy, particularly in a diverse and multicultural society like India. This paper has highlighted the critical importance of media in representing India's socio-cultural diversity, ensuring democratic participation, and fostering inclusive dialogue. A pluralistic media landscape empowers citizens, provides visibility to marginalized communities, and plays a pivotal role in conflict resolution by presenting diverse perspectives.

However, the challenges to media pluralism in India are manifold. Commercialization prioritizes sensationalism over substantive issues, while political affiliations compromise the independence and neutrality of media outlets. Technological disparities further exacerbate the digital divide, creating echo chambers and enabling the proliferation of misinformation. Additionally, regional media often struggles to compete with larger national platforms, sidelining grassroots concerns. Public discourse, mediated by these channels, reflects and amplifies these challenges, frequently marginalizing voices based on caste, religion, gender, and other socio-economic divides.

Case studies such as the farmers' protests, caste-based violence, and gendered narratives reveal how media can both illuminate and obscure societal issues. While mainstream media often aligns with dominant narratives, alternative platforms have proven their transformative potential by amplifying dissenting and marginalized voices. The #MeToo movement, for instance, demonstrated the power of digital media in challenging entrenched stereotypes and fostering global solidarity.

Media pluralism is essential for upholding democratic values, including accountability, civic engagement, and freedom of expression. Pluralistic media ensures governmental transparency, promotes participatory democracy, and protects the right to dissent. However, achieving true pluralism requires a multi-faceted approach. Policy interventions are needed to regulate monopolies and support public service broadcasting. Strengthening regional and alternative media, bridging the digital divide, combating misinformation, and promoting diversity in media representation are crucial steps.

Looking ahead, the future of media pluralism in India hinges on its ability to adapt to technological advancements while maintaining ethical journalism. Technologies like artificial intelligence and big data offer opportunities to personalize content and increase inclusivity but also pose risks related to surveillance and bias. Public discourse must evolve to address these challenges, fostering critical thinking, inclusivity, and the responsible use of technology.

In conclusion, media pluralism in India is not merely an ideal but a necessity for sustaining its democratic and multicultural identity. By addressing the challenges of commercialization, political interference, and technological disruption, and by fostering a culture of inclusivity and ethical journalism, the media can serve as a transformative force in shaping an equitable and democratic

society. Ensuring that all voices are represented and heard in public discourse is not just a matter of justice but a fundamental requirement for a thriving democracy.

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IDEOLOGY OF THE CONGRESS (I): AN ANALYSIS**Krishna Hombal**

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Abstract

There is no dirt for literature on Congress (I)'s ideology. Yet it is exponential for various reasons. Political party and ideology occupy pivotal place in vocabulary of political science. Political party as a basic brick of political system, and, ideology as a luminous set of ideas and principles are mutually interdependent. Ideology is a benchmark of party identity. Its Significance lies in its utility in the ebb and flow of politics. Legal and institutional structures and processes, plans, policies and programmes, nation's legislations and obligations to international treaties and international institutions without the guide light of an appropriate ideology would become directionless and carefree. In other words, the nature and role of every state and its policies are reinforced by a particular ideology. Similarly, Indian National Congress, as a grand old organization and a mass movement gradually evolved its ideology during and after epic struggle for national liberation. Congress (I), although born out of a split in 1969, has inherited INC's ideology. Its policies and programmes have been motivated by its ideology. It contributed a lot in determining the nature and role of the Indian state and directed its policy formation and implementation. Its ideology itself is an abstraction of the multiplicity of dynamic factors. India's colonial past, hierarchical society, problem-ridden economy, fragmented polity coupled with ethnic diversity cultural plurality and contemporary externalities are few to enumerate. At the same time, quite a few of these variables have given it essential flexibility and adaptability to implement policies and programs to govern nations in tune with ever changing domestic and international situations. More importantly, it provides analysts with an objective criterion to critically analyze and arrive at a judicious conclusion regarding Congress (I)'s ideological commitment, shifts and departures. Its Critiques have accused it of deviating from its established ideology. Hence, this serves to understand the divide between Congress (I)'s rhetoric and reality on the one hand, and, myths and realities of critiques on the other. Swadeshi, Mixed Economy, democratic socialism and self-reliance are important principals of Congress (I)'s ideology. Hence, they are found worthy of analysis in this paper.

Introduction:

There is no dirt for literature on Congress (I)'s ideology. Yet it is exponential for various reasons. Political party and ideology occupy pivotal place in vocabulary of political science. Political party as a basic brick of political system, and, ideology as a luminous set of ideas and principles are mutually interdependent. Ideology is a benchmark of party identity. Its Significance lies in its utility in the ebb and flow of politics. Legal and institutional structures and processes, plans, policies and programmes, nation's legislations and obligations to international treaties and international institutions without the guide light of an appropriate ideology would become directionless and carefree. In other words, the nature and role of every state and its policies are reinforced by a particular ideology. Similarly, Indian National Congress, as a grand old organization and a mass movement gradually evolved its ideology during and after epic struggle for national liberation. Congress (I), although born out of a split in 1969, has inherited INC's ideology. Its policies and programmes have been motivated by its ideology. It contributed a lot in determining the nature and role of the Indian state and directed its policy formation and implementation. Its ideology itself is an abstraction of the multiplicity of dynamic factors. India's colonial past, hierarchical society, problem-ridden economy, fragmented polity coupled with ethnic diversity cultural plurality and contemporary externalities are few to enumerate. At the same time, quite a few of these variables have given it essential flexibility and adaptability to implement policies and programs to govern nations in tune with ever changing domestic and international situations. More importantly, it provides analysts with an objective criterion to critically

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However, it is pertinent to note as to what ideology connotes? "According to Frank Thakurdas ideology is a type of political theory which uphold a certain political system (in its broadest sense) and the values and ideals that sustain it, as the final proximation of the human mind to an ideal arrangement and therefore, claiming this finality seeks to realize it." Daniel bell and Robert e lane declared the 'end of ideology'. For instance Daniel bell remarked: 'ideology which was once a road to actions, has come to a dead end.'

The debate on the end of ideology could not prevent the march of ideologies on the earth. What appear to be true in the context of western world especially in the American society was not true in the context of non western world. Ideology as a political parties propoganda machine continued to captivate the attention of statesman and politicians in developing and less developed countries. Political parties of the India's largest democracy could not insulate from the spellbound influence of one or the other ideology. Indian national congress and its successor party namely congress (I) are not exceptions. Even to this date in India ideologies with all their multidimensionalities and multi consequentialities are penetrating in to the hearts of the Indians during and after the elections. Hence, this paper focuses on Congress (I)'s ideology.

SWADESHI

The notion of swadeshi or economic nationalism is an offspring of Indian nationalist movement. It evolved out of its multi dimensional reaction to political and economic subjugation of repressive and exploitative colonial rule of the British imperialist government. As a movement and ideology it stood for the opposition to drain of national wealth. Its emphasis is on the promotion and protection of indigenouse resource base, economic and cultural lives against the foreign invasion and competition. It is a nation-state's arrangement to prefer local and neighborhood resources to remote ones to achieve nations over all development. In other words it is an economic system that jealously guards its nation's space, sovereignty and upholds supremacy of national interest even in the conduct of its external economic relations. In a way it denotes a universal principle policy of all nations. Hence Congress (I) too in recognition of dynamic needs, and realities and policy imperatives attempted to conceptualize swadeshi in its own way. It reiterates that the cardinal principle of its economic policy is swadeshi. It is an essential means for the realization of the nation's primary objective namely true self-reliance. For the translation of this principal and goal it claim to have embarked upon suitable policies and evolved strategies in response to emerging contingencies. To contextually conceptualize swadeshi, Congress (I) gives to it efficiency oriented connotation. "Swadeshi must mean efficiency in all respects. It can mean nothing else in this competitive world."

Self-Reliance

Earlier, in conjunction with swadeshi, self-reliance as a principal and objective has shaped INC's policies and discourse. It claims to have first put this goal before the people. Its economic construction of self-reliance is therefore accountable.

Pandit Nehru was recollected to have defined self-reliance in changed setting in first chapter of the third five-year plan document. Self-reliance, as it was then defined, was not India would become an

autarchic nation or India would become self-reliant in everything regardless of costs. “But self-reliance was defined as our capacity to finance our development through our own resources without artificial props”

Hence, INC defined ‘self-reliance’ in terms of foreign trade rather than foreign aid or debt. In its view, Self-reliance does not mean isolation and living in a cocoon. The true objectives of self-reliance are best achieved through trade, not aid and by investments, not borrowings. To the congress, “self-reliance is not a mere slogan but a cherished goal that can be achieved only when the economy develops the capacity to pay for its imports through export earnings”.

INC identified a set of following national capacities to measure True self-Reliance:

Capacity to save more and invest more; economic potentialities to create more jobs and generate more incomes; agricultural and industrial capacities to absorb more investment and better technology; The capacity to pay for the import of capital goods and raw materials; The capacity to pay for the import of essential articles like fertilizers, edible oils and petroleum products to meet the needs of the people; The capacity to repay the debt and to pay the interest charges.

Bearing all these in mind congress(I) aims at building India into an affluent, debt free and self-reliant nation.

SOCIALISM

INC’s economic ideology is enriched by socialism as well. This is the consequence of the Soviet Russia’s great socialist revolution, development through centralized planning and the impact of Gandhi’s notion of violence and exploitation free society. It inspired INC’s young leadership to dream about its adoption in free India as well. Hence, INC in its historic sessions in Karachi 1931 and in Avadi in 1955 adopted resolutions to this effect. Such resolute reiterations of commitments to socialism reflect in Nehru’s economic programmes, Five year plans, in Congress (I)’s election manifestoes and its policy actions. Besides preamble, fundamental rights, directive principles of state’s policy and several other provisions of the Constitution of India were already in place to stand straight as icons of socialism. But Till 1955 INC’s burning desire to reveal its goal to transform India into a “socialist state” had remained incognito. However, this was implicit in phrases like “cooperative Common Wealth” and “welfare state”. While Nehru’s mixed economic model of development brought out the soul of socialism, MRS Indra Gandhi’s nationalization of fourteen banks and twenty point programs brought out its dynamic and fruitful skeleton. With its incertion in the preamble of the Indian constitution by amendments in 1976 and placing it before “secularism” it in 1977, India became “sovereign, socialist, secular, democratic Republic.”

The question of central importance to this study is however, why Congress (I) reposes and reaffirms its faith in socialism or Nehruvian model of mixed economic development although its proven proclivity is toward pro capitalist policies since 1980s, and neocolonial globalization and WTO since 1991? Hindsight is in order. Although GATT initially emerged outside the Sino Soviet socialist spear; that it was (as WTO is), a capitalist oriented instrument of foreign trade policies; many socialist countries gradually joined it. Perhaps its narrower agenda and scope of jurisdiction might have attracted them. Nehru’s commitment to the principle of multilateralism and global peace and prosperity through trade cooperation drove India into GATT. Irrefutably, it joined it almost at a time when socialism and mixed economy were being crafted and grafted into the domestic political economy. But contemporary phase of globalization and WTO are so much penetrative that the autonomy of the protectionist and interventionist socialist state is endangered. This apparently exposes discrepancy between congress(i)’s advocacy for socialism and practical adherence to neo liberalism mediating

through its economic and WTO policies. This is so because; globalization and WTO's principles of economic liberalism and those of socialism are irreconcilable. Their Irreconcilability is of course a source of dilemmas and perplexities. Socialism's rhetorical appeal while promoted populism, served as a political capital for Congress (I)'s leadership's strategy to broaden, consolidate and retain its support base among poorer sections of Indian society. Its momentary abandonment in favor of economic liberalism would create an impression that Congress (I) is an institutional dehumanizer. Therefore, it must be argued that this grand old party of India without socialism is likely to fall into the poverty of philosophy. Hence, No wonder, to escape such a fall and debut the charge of ideological departure, Congress (I) reiterates and calls for the redefinition of socialism to hide what its bourgeoisie hearted capitalist bikini seeks to reveal. Congress (I)'s ideological adherence, flexibility and hoodwinking too can thus be seen through an incisive analysis.

Post independent India's leadership's perception of national and international situations was responsible for its determination to go by the middle path of economic development. It reflected in India's adoption of parliamentary democracy, socialist biased mixed economic model of development and the evolution of non alignment policy as an instrument for economic diplomacy. Problem ridden domestic society, economy and polity coupled with INC's imperative to carry forward all sections of Indian population on the one hand and the global political economy characterized by the onset of cold war between two competing ideological systems, namely, capitalism and communism, on the other, rationalized Nehru's thrust on adoption of such a course of action. He, therefore as an ardent champion of socialism revealed his position. "I stand for socialism and, I hope, India will stand for socialism and that India will go towards the constitution of a socialist state..."

AICC in its meeting in Delhi November 1947 passed resolution on the following objectives:

1. A quick and progressive rise in the standard of living and the achievement of a national minimum standard in respect of all essentials of physical and social well-being within a reasonable period.
2. Affording opportunities for full employment, which should result in fuller utilization of manpower, especially on land and in rural industries.
3. An expanding volume of production.
4. Equitable distribution of the existing income and wealth and prevention of the growth of disparities.
5. The economic organization of the country should function on a decentralized basis to secure the widest diffusion of opportunities for gainful occupation of a suitable character and to reduce to the minimum opportunities for exploitation

AICC was aware of a need for the establishment of an appropriate political system for the realization of its defined objectives. Hence it declared its intention in the instant Resolution. "Our aim should be to evolve a political system, which will combine efficiency of administration with individual liberty and an economic structure, which will yield maximum production without the creation of private monopolies and the concentration of wealth and which will proper balance between urban and rural economies. Such a social structure can provide an alternative to the acquisitive economy of private capitalism and the regimentation of the totalitarian state."

In pursuance of this resolution, AICC appointed a committee headed by Jawaharlal Nehru to draw up an economic programme. Subsequently it approved Both Nehru's recommendations and the industrial policy resolution of 6th April 1948 in its Jaipur session. Recommended program and industrial policy resolution were both democratic and socialist in orientation. They favored "Mixed Economy".

Their primary purpose was to promote state's ownership, control and regulation of large and key industries in the national interest without affecting legitimate interests of the private industrialists. System based on mixed economic model of development was a well thought out solution to the problems of India's Iniquitous social and economic order. To setup an egalitarian society with economic growth with equity, social and economic justice was visualized. Arguably, therefore, state intervention of this kind was a sine qua non for effective harmonization and resolution of conflicting interests and balance the wide variety of radical and conservative forces. Leaders thought that it would be impossible to arrest possible fall of just born India into a chaotic order without grafting such an alternative. Their time tested foresight bore fruit in January, 1955's AICC's historic session at Avadi in Madras.

This session and its resolution are historic for their progressive crystallization of Indian brand of socialism and socialist vision for the construction of Indian society and economy. Its following resolution evidences this. "In order to realize the objective of the congress as laid down in Article 1 of the congress Constitution and to further the objectives, stated in the preamble and Directive Principles of state Policy of the constitution of India, planning should take place with view to the establishment of a socialistic pattern of society, where the principal means of production are under social ownership or control, production is progressively speeded up and there is equitable distribution of the national wealth."

The socialistic pattern was explained in another resolution on economic policy, which declared, inter alia: - in view of the declared objective being a socialist pattern of society, the state will necessarily play a vital part in planning and development. In particular, it will: - (i) initiate and operate large-scale schemes providing services such as power, transport, etc.; (ii) Have overall control of resources, social purposes and trades, and essential balances in economy; (iii) check and prevent evils of anarchic industrial development by the maintenance of standards of labour and production' (iv) plan the economy of the nation in its basic and broad aspects."

Nehru in AICC's open session before moving the resolution in Avadi vociferously declared that the primary purpose for the adoption of socialism was to establish welfare state and socialist society. He visualized that welfare state and socialist society are intrinsically interpenetrative. Hence, he argued, "The welfare state is an essential part of the socialist pattern. ... We must look at the ideal and should be governed by that ideal and that pattern."

The instant session is significant for yet another reason. In his presidential address, U.N. Dhebar, laid a foundation for the conceptualization and construction of democratic socialism in land a of conservative capitalism dominated by Zamindhars and private industrialists. He signaled after a Gandhian fashion a peaceful transformation through a non-violent revolution achievable through democratic socialism. While enunciating the underlying idea of socialism he imparted socio, economic and normative dynamism to the notion of democracy. "It is generally accepted that political democracy is unthinkable without social democracy, and it is also generally realized that any momentum in our progress is unthinkable, unless an atmosphere of a common undertaking and common sacrifice is created.... genuine equality is unthinkable unless equal opportunities are made available to every citizen of India. In the new social order that we envisage, the difference in advantages between citizen and citizen will have to be distinction on the ground of one's avocation."

Rhetorical Ideology without target specific efficacies is just a political sterility. Because, Socialist policies and programs avowedly promised and vigorously implemented in pre emergency period built up infrastructure more for the affluent than for the poor. Sad to political, bureaucratic and state owned industrial managerial elites' lack of commitment, democratic socialism was turned out to

be in fructuous. Populist poverty alleviation programs like Garibi Hatao were not implemented justiciably either in pre emergency or in post emergency periods. Administrative inefficiency, PSUs' lack of quality and productivity, resource depletion, economic stagnation and sluggish economic growth were staring into the eyes of Indian political economy. Consequently, socialism in post emergency politics has been reduced into a just an appealing political slogan to murder paper producing bamboos.

Almost all post emergency governments at the center ranging from Janata to the Congress (I) led UPA brought a drastic change in India's policy environment. They began to drift away from socialism for reasons of domestic and global politico economic necessities. Janata's business class friendly policies while laid foundation for economic liberalism, they sowed seeds of frustration with socialism. MRS Indira Gandhi's imperative to woo and win back traditional business class support from Hindi heartland for political and power consolidation motivated her to stealthily deviate from Nehruvian model of socialism during 1980-84. Rajeev Gandhi was bent upon following the foot prints of his mother during 1984-87. Despite his love for corporate friendly economic liberalism he opposed wholesale rejectionist approach to socialism in favour of market forces. Not only he advocated for its utility for genuine beneficiaries but also called for its redefinition to serve in future. He argued, "...we see that socialism is being thrown out completely, for capitalist market forces. ... Socialism must have a new definition which relates to the uplift of the poorest and weaker sections..."

But his successor, Shri P V Narasimha Rao when became prime minister aided by his finance minister and erstwhile bureaucrat, namely, Manmohan Singh's economic advice tried to define its dynamic doom. PVN was aware of the situation in which Nehru crafted mixed economic model of development and its virtues. Hence, His heartfelt obituary to it is contextually demanding. "When communist ideas tended to overpower Indian thinking, Prime Minister Nehru adumbrated the concept of 'Mixed economy'. He was criticized in every quarter, right and left; but mixed economy concept has saved India time and again, from political submission and economic dependence."

Similarly, Congress (I) upheld its relevance for the south. It argued, "The adoption of the mixed economy model by practically all developing economies and by most of the so called Asian Tiger Economies only serves to re-emphasise the importance of Nehruvian thinking today."

Deeds not the ideological assertions are reliable definitions. Since 1991 Congress (I) 's leadership is obsessed with neo liberal processes like liberalization, privatization and globalization. It's Economic and pro WTO policies have strengthened India's credentials as a reckonable neo liberal bourgeoisie state. They disfigure socialist face of mixed economic model of development. Gradual privatization of public sector units and corporatisation of Indian economy transform Indian state into a market friendly state rather than a poorer friendly socialist state. Notwithstanding Congress (I) defined its version of socialism as "dynamic socialism".

Its task force justifies that "Congress (I)'s economic reforms are in consistent with socialism as they generate resources for the effective implementation of developmental programs for the benefit of the poor."

In short, frequent talk of reforms with human face will neither restore socialism its pristine glory nor will it shield Congress (I) from the vilification Congress (I) is the grand old party that diluted its socialist ideology to comfort domestic and global capitalist forces at the expense of its masses.

Over and above congress(I)'s has abiding faith in luminous set of ideas and principals which may be enumerated as under :

Ghandism, Constitutionalism, secularism, religious harmony, unity in diversity, multiculturalism, democratic socialism, inclusive nationalism, social justice and welfare state . congress (I) foreign policy

like its predecessors is guided by anticolonialism, anti-imperialism, anti raceism , Non-alignment, multilateralism, promotion of international peace and equitable world order and abiding faith in united nations. Thus the comprehensive and multi dimensional nature of congress (I)'s ideology is bridging the centuries in the perpetual ebb and flow of india's domestic and global politics .

Conclusion

In the context of India's largest liberal multi party democracy, debate on end of ideology is irrational and irrelevant. Ideology is source of inspiration and guidance for Indian national congress in the past and congress(I) at present. but principals like swadeshi, self reliance and socialism have been reoriented on account of globalization . Explosion of population coupled with revolution in expectations has brought about tremendous changes in India's competitive power politics. Any ideology is not an end in itself. It is a means for power configuration, party building and nation building. Congress (I) s departure from Gandhian and nehruvian principals and ideals of swadeshi and socialism has been occasioned by constraints and compulsions of domestic and global political economy.

But moorings of its political ideology like secularism, inclusive nationalism social justice, welfare state and ideals of foreign policy are still holding ground. Congress (I) led UPA governments schemes like MNREGA, Food security Act, and five guarantee schemes implemented in Karnataka bear testimony to its commitment to socialism. However, power phallic aspirations of the politicians should not eclipse the luminosity of the ideology in favor of nihilistic populism and sheer vote bank politics. Taxing everything including breath, blood, sweat and life for resource mobilization would turn democracy in to kleptocracy and development or welfare state in to a Frankenstein state. Choice is neither with the chance, nor with the chisel, but with the people who vote to elect their representatives and rulers during elections. Ideology is just a fig leaf alas!!!

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VIABILITY AND CONSEQUENCES OF IMPLEMENTING ONE NATION, ONE ELECTION IN INDIA

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Abstract

This research article delves into the One Nation, One Election initiative in India, aiming to assess its practicality and broader implications. By examining the concept of simultaneous elections across all tiers of government, the study highlights potential benefits such as cost efficiency and streamlined governance. However, it also addresses significant hurdles, including constitutional challenges and the complexities of coordinating election logistics. The analysis extends to the effects on democratic integrity, political party strategies, and voter participation. Through a comprehensive review of legal frameworks and practical considerations, this research provides a nuanced understanding of the initiative's potential impact. Ultimately, it offers informed recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders, guiding them in their evaluation of this transformative electoral proposal.

Keywords: One Nation One Election, India, electoral reform, simultaneous elections, democratic principles, political parties, voter behavior, constitutional challenges, governance efficiency, policy recommendations.

1. Introduction

The proposal of "One Nation, One Election" (ONOE) suggests conducting simultaneous elections for India's Lok Sabha (the lower house of Parliament) and all state legislative assemblies every five years. By aligning electoral cycles at the national and state levels, ONOE aims to streamline the election process, reducing both the frequency of elections and the disruptions they bring to governance. Local body elections and by-elections, however, would remain unaffected. The concept of synchronized elections is not new to India; from 1951 to 1967, elections for both the Lok Sabha and state assemblies were held together. However, this pattern was disrupted due to early dissolutions of certain assemblies and the Lok Sabha itself, which led to a staggered election process that has persisted for decades.

Interest in ONOE has grown significantly in recent years, particularly under the administration of Prime Minister Narendra Modi, who has championed this reform since taking office in 2014. The Law Commission of India first presented ONOE in a 1999 report, and the concept was later revived in 2017 in a discussion paper by NITI Aayog, authored by Bibek Debroy and Kishore Desai. The paper highlighted the potential of simultaneous elections to address "policy paralysis," a situation that arises due to the Model Code of Conduct, which restricts government actions during elections. Advocates of ONOE argue that synchronized elections could minimize this disruption and streamline governance, allowing governments to maintain consistent policy and focus on development over prolonged election cycles.

Proponents also argue that ONOE could result in substantial cost savings, significantly lowering the financial burden of frequent elections. For instance, the Election Commission of India reported that the 2019 general elections alone cost over ₹4,000 crore. Supporters believe that conducting elections concurrently would reduce administrative and logistical costs, enabling government resources to be more efficiently allocated toward governance. Beyond cost savings, proponents suggest that ONOE would simplify the electoral process and reduce continuous campaigning, which could enhance governance and create a more consistent political environment. However, despite its potential benefits,

ONOE has sparked considerable debate regarding its broader implications for India's federal structure and democratic integrity.

Critics of ONOE argue that the reform may pose challenges to federalism, potentially leading to a concentration of power and undermining regional representation. There is concern that national issues may overshadow local issues in elections, which could disadvantage regional parties and alter the dynamics of political representation. Additionally, the implementation of ONOE would require major constitutional amendments and the development of a political consensus, both of which present significant obstacles. As discussions continue, it is evident that ONOE represents a significant departure from India's current electoral framework and would require comprehensive reforms for successful implementation. This article provides a detailed review of the ONOE proposal, examining its historical context, potential benefits, challenges, and implications for India's democratic landscape.

2. Advantages of One Nation, One Election

The One Nation, One Election (ONOE) initiative proposes synchronizing elections for India's Lok Sabha and all state legislative assemblies every five years. This approach is designed to streamline the electoral process, offering significant benefits in terms of cost savings, improved governance, and administrative efficiency.

2.1. Cost Efficiency

A primary advantage of ONOE is the potential for substantial cost savings. Conducting individual elections requires considerable financial outlay on logistics, such as deploying security forces, setting up polling booths, transporting Electronic Voting Machines (EVMs), and organizing voter outreach programs. By consolidating all elections into one process, ONOE could significantly reduce these recurring expenses. Estimates suggest that synchronized elections could save around ₹4,500 crores compared to the current system of staggered elections, easing the financial burden on both the government and political parties, particularly smaller regional ones that often face resource constraints. Furthermore, the consolidation of elections would allow better allocation of security and administrative resources, as fewer elections would mean fewer instances of diverting personnel and high-ranking officials to manage electoral processes, improving resource availability for public service delivery.

2.2. Governance Improvement

ONOE could also improve governance by reducing the disruptions caused by frequent elections. The Model Code of Conduct (MCC), which is enforced during election periods, restricts governments from announcing new policies. If elections were held simultaneously every five years, the MCC would be in effect less frequently, allowing governments to focus on sustained governance without the regular interruptions of election cycles. This shift could support more stable and consistent policy-making at both central and state levels. Additionally, ONOE could encourage higher voter turnout, as a single election event would simplify participation in the democratic process. Higher turnout could increase the legitimacy of elected officials and promote a focus on long-term policy goals over short-term, populist measures targeted at imminent elections.

2.3. Administrative Efficiency

By reducing the frequency of elections, ONOE could enhance administrative efficiency. Current election cycles require extensive mobilization of resources and personnel for management and security, which can strain the administrative apparatus. A synchronized electoral cycle would streamline these demands, allowing government agencies to focus more consistently on delivering essential services. This stability would enable more effective planning and implementation of development projects that might otherwise be disrupted by election-related MCC restrictions. Moreover, ONOE could also

improve internal security management by minimizing the need for repeated deployment of security forces, thereby freeing these resources to address pressing security needs across the country.

The ONOE initiative presents a compelling case for transforming India's electoral landscape. By promoting cost savings, enhancing governance focus, and improving administrative efficiency, ONOE offers a potential path toward a more sustainable and effective democratic process.

3. Challenges and Criticisms of One Nation, One Election

ONOE initiative proposes synchronizing elections for India's Lok Sabha and all state legislative assemblies every five years. Despite support for its potential advantages, ONOE faces notable challenges and criticisms that warrant thorough examination.

3.1. Constitutional and Legal Hurdles

One of the core challenges of ONOE is the constitutional and legal restructuring it requires. Implementing simultaneous elections would necessitate amendments to key legal provisions, such as Articles 83, 172, and 356 of the Indian Constitution, to align the election cycles across all levels of government. Achieving the political consensus needed for these changes is a significant hurdle, especially in India's diverse political landscape.

Additionally, concerns about federalism and state autonomy are central to the debate. Opponents argue that aligning election schedules could centralize power and undermine the autonomy of state governments. This is especially concerning in India, where local dynamics play a critical role in electoral outcomes, and where states may feel that their specific political contexts could be overshadowed by a national agenda that does not fully represent local issues or the voices of regional parties.

3.2. Political Implications

The political implications of ONOE are another area of concern. Some critics suggest that synchronized elections could favor larger national parties, potentially overshadowing smaller, regional parties that focus on local issues. This shift could alter the balance of representation, reducing the voice of regional interests and diminishing political diversity, which many marginalized communities rely on to have their specific concerns addressed through their representatives.

Further, ONOE raises risks of centralization. With national and state elections held at the same time, there is a risk that national narratives could dominate, potentially sidelining local issues and stifling grassroots movements. This centralization may limit the diversity of political representation and diminish the variety of perspectives within legislative bodies.

3.3. Voter Behavior and Engagement

ONOE may also impact voter behavior and engagement. While proponents argue that simultaneous elections might improve voter turnout by making participation simpler, there are concerns that it could lead to the opposite effect. With multiple elections combined, voters might experience fatigue or confusion, potentially disengaging from the electoral process. Critics fear that merging national and state elections could reduce voter enthusiasm, which is already challenged by the frequency and complexity of elections in India.

Additionally, there is concern about representation of local issues. If state and national elections are held concurrently, the focus on national issues may overshadow critical local concerns. This shift could discourage voters from engaging in state elections, particularly if they perceive that their specific regional interests are being subordinated to broader national priorities.

ONOE initiative represents a bold approach to reforming India's electoral system, but it also brings significant challenges. Constitutional amendments are a considerable obstacle, and issues related to

federalism and state autonomy underscore potential risks to local governance. Politically, synchronized elections could alter the balance of representation, potentially benefiting larger national parties over regional ones. Additionally, concerns about voter behavior and local representation suggest that careful consideration is needed to avoid disenfranchising certain segments of the electorate. As ONOE continues to be debated, addressing these challenges is crucial for ensuring that any implementation aligns with India's complex democratic structure.

4. Recommendations from Committees and Experts on One Nation, One Election

The One Nation, One Election (ONOE) proposal, which aims to synchronize elections for the Lok Sabha and all state legislative assemblies, has prompted in-depth analysis from political leaders, experts, and committees. These discussions highlight both the potential benefits of ONOE and its key challenges, offering a structured approach to implementing this significant reform.

4.1. Summary of Key Recommendations from the High-Level Committee

In September 2023, the Indian government established a High-Level Committee on One Nation, One Election, chaired by former President Ram Nath Kovind, to assess ONOE's feasibility and gather input from political parties and public stakeholders. Among the committee's recommendations are:

Constitutional Amendments: Implementing ONOE would require amendments to Articles 83, 85, 172, 174, and 356 of the Indian Constitution. These changes are essential to align the terms of the Lok Sabha and state assemblies and clarify the President's dissolution powers.

Phased Implementation: Given the complexity of conducting simultaneous elections, the committee recommended a phased approach, beginning with synchronizing elections at a limited level and expanding gradually to national and state levels.

Stakeholder Engagement: Broad engagement with constitutional experts, election officials, think tanks, and political party representatives is necessary to ensure diverse perspectives are included in drafting amendments and addressing practical concerns.

Logistical Preparedness: The committee recommended increasing the supply of Electronic Voting Machines (EVMs) and voter-verifiable paper audit trail (VVPAT) units to ensure the logistical needs of simultaneous elections are met. Planning for adequate resources and infrastructure is critical to manage such a nationwide electoral process.

4.2. Perspectives from Political Leaders and Stakeholders

ONOE has sparked a range of responses from political leaders, reflecting both support for and concerns about the initiative's potential impact on India's democratic processes.

4.2.1. Indian National Congress Opinions about ONOE

The Indian National Congress (INC) has expressed strong opposition to the One Nation, One Election (ONOE) initiative, articulating concerns about its implications for democracy, federalism, and local representation. Here are some key opinions from INC leaders regarding ONOE:

Adhir Ranjan Chowdhury: The former leader of the Congress in the Lok Sabha has been vocal in his criticism, labeling the ONOE proposal as a "total eyewash." He argues that the initiative undermines the essence of democracy by prioritizing a fixed electoral calendar over the will of the people. Chowdhury emphasizes that elections should reflect the citizens' trust in their representatives, which can change at any time, rather than being constrained by a predetermined schedule.

Sonia Gandhi: The former president of the INC has raised concerns about how ONOE could disproportionately benefit larger national parties like the BJP and Congress at the expense of regional parties. She has highlighted that this could lead to a dilution of local issues, which are crucial for state

elections. Gandhi argues that regional parties play an essential role in representing local interests and that simultaneous elections could marginalize these voices.

Mallikarjun Kharge: The current president of the INC has articulated that ONOE poses significant threats to India's federal structure. He argues that it would centralize power and diminish the autonomy of state governments, thereby undermining India's diversity and democratic ethos. Kharge believes that each state should have the freedom to conduct its elections based on its unique political landscape.

Yogendra Yadav: While not an INC member but a prominent political activist and former member of the Aam Aadmi Party (AAP), Yadav has echoed similar sentiments regarding ONOE. He describes it as a "fantasy" of the ruling elite to simplify democracy at the expense of its complexity. Yadav criticizes the consultations conducted by the High-Level Committee for being insufficiently inclusive and argues that they failed to capture the diverse opinions across India.

P.D.T. Achary: A former secretary-general of the Lok Sabha, Achary has supported the INC's position by questioning the financial rationale behind ONOE. He points out that while proponents claim it will reduce election costs, political parties spend significantly more on campaigns than what is allocated for conducting elections. Achary argues that if reducing expenditure is genuinely a concern, then state funding for elections should be considered instead.

Editorials from Congress-aligned publications: Various editorials have criticized ONOE as a "stratagem" to impose a unitary vision on India's diverse political landscape. They argue that elections should not be viewed as interruptions to governance but rather as essential expressions of public will that must be respected.

The Indian National Congress has articulated a comprehensive critique of the One Nation, One Election initiative, emphasizing concerns about federalism, local representation, and democratic integrity. The party's leadership believes that any electoral reform must prioritize inclusivity and respect for India's diverse political realities rather than impose a uniform electoral framework that could undermine regional voices and issues.

4.2.2. Bhartiya Janata Party Opinions about ONOE

The Bhartiya Janata Party (BJP) has been a strong proponent of the ONOE initiative, advocating for simultaneous elections for the Lok Sabha and all state legislative assemblies. The party argues that this approach could streamline the electoral process, reduce costs, and enhance governance. Here are some key opinions and perspectives from BJP leaders regarding ONOE:

Amit Shah: As the Home Minister and a prominent BJP leader, Shah has consistently supported ONOE, framing it as a necessary reform to reduce the frequency of elections that disrupt governance. He argues that simultaneous elections would allow governments to focus on development rather than constant campaigning. Shah believes that this initiative aligns with the party's vision of a more efficient political system.

Narendra Modi: The Prime Minister has also endorsed ONOE, suggesting that it could lead to significant cost savings for the government and political parties alike. Modi has emphasized that reducing the electoral burden will allow for better governance and more effective implementation of policies. He views ONOE as a step toward modernizing India's electoral framework.

Ram Nath Kovind Committee: The recommendations from the committee headed by former President Ram Nath Kovind have provided a formal endorsement of ONOE. The committee proposed constitutional amendments to facilitate simultaneous elections, arguing that this would enhance stability and accountability in governance. The BJP has used these recommendations to bolster its case for implementing ONOE.

Support from BJP Allies: Some allies within the National Democratic Alliance (NDA) have expressed tentative support for ONOE, viewing it as a way to consolidate power at both national and state levels. However, there is also apprehension among smaller regional parties about how this initiative might affect their electoral prospects.

Countering Criticism: In response to criticism regarding potential centralization of power and undermining federalism, BJP leaders assert that ONOE does not diminish state autonomy but rather enhances efficiency in governance. They argue that India's diverse political landscape can still be respected within a framework of synchronized elections.

Public Messaging: The BJP has framed ONOE as a response to public demand for more efficient governance. Party leaders often highlight how frequent elections lead to voter fatigue and distract from pressing issues facing the nation.

Concerns Over Implementation: Despite strong advocacy for ONOE, some BJP leaders acknowledge the challenges in achieving consensus among various political factions. There are concerns about securing the necessary constitutional amendments, given the current composition of Parliament and opposition from non-BJP parties.

The BJP's stance on One Nation, One Election is rooted in its vision of creating a more streamlined and efficient electoral process that prioritizes governance over perpetual campaigning. While there is enthusiasm within the party for the potential benefits of ONOE, challenges related to implementation and broader political consensus remain significant hurdles to its realization.

5. Implementation Strategies for One Nation, One Election

The One Nation, One Election (ONOE) initiative proposes synchronizing elections for India's Lok Sabha and all state legislative assemblies, aiming to reshape the electoral process by promoting efficiency and reducing election frequency. To implement this ambitious initiative, experts suggest strategies that include a phased approach and fostering broad-based national dialogue among stakeholders.

5.1. Phased Approach to Implementation

A phased approach is seen as vital for the successful rollout of ONOE. Key elements of this approach include:

Pilot Programs for Testing ONOE: Implementing pilot programs in select states or regions can serve as an effective initial step. By testing the logistics and procedures of simultaneous elections, these pilot programs can provide valuable data on challenges such as voter behavior, administrative logistics, and security measures. For instance, states with similar electoral cycles could be selected to assess impacts and fine-tune strategies based on observed voter response and administrative efficiency.

Timeline for Full Implementation: Establishing a structured timeline is crucial to ensure a steady progression toward national-level implementation. This timeline could encompass several years and outline key stages, such as constitutional amendments, completion of pilot programs, and gradual synchronization of elections across levels. A staggered approach provides flexibility, allowing adequate time for preparing resources, making adjustments, and gaining consensus from all involved stakeholders.

5.2. National Dialogue and Consensus Building

Building national consensus through dialogue is another critical component of ONOE implementation. Fostering agreement across political and civil society groups can pave the way for smoother adoption and address concerns comprehensively.

Engaging Political Parties: Including political parties in structured discussions around ONOE is essential for establishing common ground. Consultations, workshops, and forums allow party leaders to share concerns, including potential impacts on regional representation. Acknowledging these perspectives helps address concerns of regional parties about marginalization and enables the formation of a more balanced framework that respects both local and national interests.

Involving Civil Society: Civil society organizations, think tanks, and electoral experts play a key role in bringing diverse viewpoints to the discussion. Their insights on voter behavior, logistical requirements, and potential challenges can help shape a well-rounded approach to ONOE. Public awareness campaigns, meanwhile, can educate citizens on ONOE's benefits, fostering greater understanding and support among the electorate.

Addressing Concerns Over Local Representation: A significant criticism of ONOE is its potential to overshadow regional issues in favor of national narratives. To mitigate this, stakeholders can examine evidence showing that Indian voters typically differentiate between national and state elections. By addressing concerns that synchronized elections may weaken local representation, supporters can build confidence that the reform respects the diversity of India's political landscape.

Implementing the One Nation, One Election initiative will require a carefully designed strategy combining a phased approach with pilot programs, a well-defined timeline, and active engagement across political and civil society groups. Through a collaborative, inclusive process, India can work toward implementing this reform while enhancing its democratic processes and addressing diverse regional interests effectively.

6. Conclusion

The ONOE initiative presents a transformative approach to India's electoral process, aiming to synchronize elections for the Lok Sabha and all state legislative assemblies. As discussions around ONOE progress, it is essential to summarize the findings and consider the feasibility of this significant reform. The ONOE initiative offers several potential advantages, including cost efficiency, improved governance, and enhanced administrative efficiency. By consolidating elections into a single event every five years, the initiative could drastically reduce logistical expenses associated with conducting separate elections. This includes savings on security deployment, polling logistics, and administrative resources. Furthermore, ONOE aims to alleviate election fatigue among voters and political parties, allowing governments to focus on long-term policy implementation rather than short-term electoral strategies.

However, the proposal also faces considerable challenges. Constitutional and legal hurdles must be addressed, including necessary amendments to existing laws that govern electoral processes. Concerns about federalism and the potential marginalization of regional issues pose significant obstacles to gaining broad political consensus. Critics argue that simultaneous elections could centralize power and diminish local representation, as national narratives may overshadow regional concerns.

The feasibility of implementing ONOE hinges on several factors. First, achieving a broad-based political consensus is crucial. Engaging with various political parties and stakeholders will be essential for addressing concerns related to federalism and regional representation. The High-Level Committee's recommendations emphasize the need for constitutional amendments and phased implementation strategies, which could facilitate a smoother transition to synchronized elections.

Moreover, public support for ONOE will play a vital role in its success. As indicated by various surveys, a significant portion of the electorate appears to favor the initiative, recognizing its potential benefits in reducing election-related disruptions. However, this support must be translated into actionable policies

that address the logistical complexities of conducting simultaneous elections across India's diverse political landscape. While the One Nation, One Election initiative presents an opportunity for significant reform in India's electoral system, careful consideration of its challenges and implications is necessary. Balancing national interests with regional representation will be critical in ensuring that ONOE enhances rather than undermines India's democratic processes. With thoughtful planning and stakeholder engagement, ONOE could pave the way for a more efficient and responsive governance model that aligns with the aspirations of Indian citizens.

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CASTE POLITICS IN KARNATAKA: AN ANALYSIS**Dr. Shanthamma T R**

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Abstract

Caste politics has significantly influenced the socio-political landscape of Karnataka, shaping electoral strategies, policy decisions, and social dynamics. The state's political narrative has long been marked by the influence of dominant caste groups, such as the Lingayats and Vokkaligas, alongside marginalized communities, including Other Backward Classes (OBCs), Scheduled Castes (SCs), and Scheduled Tribes (STs). Historically, the Congress Party maintained a broad coalition, leveraging support from major caste groups. However, over the decades, the rise of regional and caste-based parties, notably the Janata Dal (Secular) [JD(S)] and the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), has transformed the political equation. The BJP's consolidation of Lingayat support and outreach to OBCs and Dalits, contrasted with the Congress's Ahinda strategy for marginalized groups, underscores the evolving caste-based alignments. Caste politics has empowered underrepresented communities, ensured greater political representation and addressed community-specific needs. Nonetheless, it has also reinforced social divisions, contributing to identity politics that sometimes overshadow broader developmental goals. Balancing these caste interests while promoting inclusive growth remains a challenge for policymakers. This analysis seeks to provide a nuanced understanding of how caste dynamics continue to shape Karnataka's political environment, influencing both electoral outcomes and governance priorities.

Keywords: Politics, Vokkaliga, Lingayat, Ahinda, Scheduled Caste, Scheduled Tribe, Barathiya Janata Party, Congress, Election.

Introduction

In Indian society, caste has had a crucial role in determining its social, political, and economic climate. This is also true of the southern Indian state of Karnataka, which has a rich cultural heritage. In Karnataka, caste politics has had a big impact on social dynamics, policy creation, and election results. The main caste groupings and their political affiliations, the historical foundations of caste politics in Karnataka, its development over time, and its effects on current politics are all examined in this research study.

Since before independence, Karnataka's intricate caste system has shaped the state's political climate. In order to question the strict caste system and advance equality throughout the colonial era, social reform movements were spearheaded by figures like Basavanna in the 12th century and more recently by reformers in the 20th century. These movements' influence prepared the way for later caste-based political mobilization. The Congress Party initially controlled Karnataka's political landscape in the years following independence. The party successfully used the backing of powerful castes like the Lingayats and Vokkaligas. However, new political alignments developed as other excluded groups became more politically conscious. By organizing different caste groups, caste-based regional organizations and leaders emerged in the post-1970s era, challenging the Congress's hegemony.

Major Caste Groups and Their Political Influence.

Karnataka's caste structure is marked by a diverse array of communities, including the dominant Vokkaligas and Lingayats, Other Backward Classes (OBCs), Scheduled Castes (SCs), and Scheduled Tribes (STs). Each of these groups has played a significant role in shaping the state's political narrative.

Lingayats: The Lingayats are one of the most influential communities in Karnataka, particularly in the northern and central parts of the state. Historically, they have supported the Congress Party, but in the late 20th century, their allegiance shifted towards the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP). The Lingayat community's support has been pivotal for the BJP's growth in Karnataka. The demand for recognition of Lingayats as a separate religion has further deepened their political significance.

Vokkaligas: The Vokkaligas, primarily concentrated in the southern districts of Karnataka, have traditionally aligned with the Janata Dal (Secular) [JD(S)]. Their support base has been essential for the party's electoral successes, particularly in the Old Mysore region. The influence of prominent Vokkaliga leaders, such as H.D. Deve Gowda, has ensured the community's continued political relevance.

Other Backward Classes (OBCs): The OBCs form a significant portion of the population and have diverse sub-groups with varying political leanings. While some OBC sub-groups have allied with the Congress, others have found representation in the BJP and JD(S). The 1990s Mandal Commission's implementation spurred OBC political mobilization, leading to greater representation in state politics.

Scheduled Castes (SCs) and Scheduled Tribes (STs): The SCs and STs have historically been marginalized but have gained political representation through reservation policies and targeted outreach programs by major political parties. The Congress has traditionally been strong among SCs, while the BJP has made significant inroads by cultivating Dalit leaders and incorporating their demands into the party's platform.

Evolution of Caste Politics.

The evolution of caste politics in Karnataka can be traced through distinct phases marked by shifts in political alignments and strategies. The period from the 1950s to the 1970s was characterized by Congress's dominance, with its ability to maintain a broad coalition of castes, including the dominant Vokkaligas and Lingayats. The 1980s marked the decline of the Congress's monopoly as regional parties like the JD(S) gained traction by championing the interests of specific caste groups.

The 1990s witnessed significant changes with the rise of the BJP as a major political force, bolstered by the support of Lingayats and sections of OBCs. The party's emphasis on Hindutva ideology resonated with certain communities, allowing it to expand its base. Meanwhile, the Congress sought to reassert its influence by appealing to marginalized groups and consolidating its SC and ST support base. The early 2000s saw heightened competition among political parties to capture the support of key caste constituencies. Alliances and coalitions shifted as parties adapted to changing demographics and political aspirations. The emergence of leaders like Siddaramaiah, who positioned himself as a champion of the backward classes, underscored the importance of caste-based identity in electoral politics.

Caste-Based Political Strategies and Electoral Outcomes

Political parties in Karnataka have employed various strategies to secure caste-based support. These strategies include candidate selection, alliances, and targeted policy initiatives. The following sections outline key tactics employed by major political players: **Candidate Selection:** Political parties have often chosen candidates based on their caste affiliation to ensure alignment with the dominant caste demographics of a particular constituency. This strategy has been particularly evident in regions where the Vokkaliga and Lingayat communities hold sway.

The formation of alliances with regional and caste-based parties has been a common practice. The JD(S), for instance, has positioned itself as a party representing Vokkaliga interests and has forged coalitions to extend its reach.

Targeted policies, such as reservation in education and employment, have been leveraged to appeal to OBCs, SCs, and STs. The Congress and BJP have both introduced welfare schemes aimed at improving the socio-economic conditions of marginalized groups. These policies have often been designed to solidify electoral support among these communities.

Recent years have seen shifts in the caste-political landscape, influenced by changing social dynamics and economic aspirations. The BJP's efforts to consolidate its position among the Lingayats, while making inroads among OBCs and Dalits, have contributed to its stronghold in Karnataka. However, issues such as internal caste rivalries, demands for increased reservation, and regional disparities continue to pose challenges.

The Congress, under leaders like Siddaramaiah, has aimed to rejuvenate its traditional support base by advocating for the "Ahinda" (an acronym for minorities, backward classes, and Dalits) strategy. This approach seeks to unify marginalized groups and position the Congress as a party of social justice. Meanwhile, the JD(S) continues to retain its influence in Vokkaliga-dominated regions but faces the challenge of expanding its appeal beyond its core base.

Implications of Caste Politics

The implications of caste politics in Karnataka extend beyond electoral outcomes. Caste-based politics has influenced policy decisions, social cohesion, and development priorities. On one hand, caste mobilization has empowered historically marginalized groups by ensuring representation and addressing their specific needs. On the other hand, it has also reinforced social divisions, contributing to competitive identity politics.

Critics argue that caste-based politics can undermine broader issues such as economic development, governance, and communal harmony. The focus on caste identity has sometimes led to the neglect of policy initiatives that benefit society as a whole. Balancing caste-based demands with the need for inclusive development remains a key challenge for policymakers.

Conclusion

Caste politics in Karnataka is a multifaceted phenomenon shaped by historical legacies, evolving political strategies, and the socio-economic landscape. The interplay between major caste groups and political parties has influenced the state's electoral dynamics and policy decisions. While caste-based mobilization has provided a platform for marginalized communities to voice their concerns, it has also perpetuated identity politics that can hinder collective progress. Understanding the nuances of caste politics in Karnataka is essential for fostering a more inclusive and equitable political landscape. Caste politics has empowered underrepresented communities, ensuring greater political representation and addressing community-specific needs. Nonetheless, it has also reinforced social divisions, contributing to identity politics that sometimes overshadow broader developmental goals. Balancing these caste interests while promoting inclusive growth remains a challenge for policymakers. This analysis seeks to provide a nuanced understanding of how caste dynamics continue to shape Karnataka's political environment, influencing both electoral outcomes and governance priorities.

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ONE NATION ONE ELECTION: IMPACT ON DEMOCRACY AND FEDERAL STRUCTURE OF INDIA AN EMPIRICAL STUDY**Dr. Nagaraju. N**

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Abstract

One nation one election is the most debating constitutional issue across the nation. The issues are discussed in various levels, like political parties, medias and press and more importantly it has been debated in academic arena as a subject of constitutional issues and challenges to Indian democracy. The continuous election to parliament and assemblies is contemporary issues; most importantly it is a destructive attempt of ruling government to erosion of socio-political fabric of federal structure of India. The one nation one election has no national or public interest it has vested interest of replacing democracy by unified centralized system. The concept of one nation one election has been proposed and advocated by NDA government specially BJP, BJP has declared "One Nation One Election" as its political manifesto in 2014 parliament election and accordingly it has appointed study committee, headed by former president of India Ram Nath Kovind, the committee has submitted its report to union government and made recommendation for required amendment to constitution in respect of "One Nation One Election". The objectives of one nation one election is to cutting economic burden on nation, the BJP put forwarded question is we are spent lot of money on various election to parliament and states assemblies while holding election at different stages, meanwhile administrative machinery has always engages in conducting various election, due to this continuous election process and work, administration has not give their proper attention to the development work it is set back to the national development, obviously administration plays key role in nation building and bringing socio-economic transformation particularly total development of nation and people, it is time to introspect and retrospect efficiency and effectiveness of administration how it has performed its duties. Our executive, in the true sense, the government priority is make administration into effective and accountable for their function rather than one election because people lost their faith on administration, administration has not motive of vision or goal oriented therefore public money has misused and plan, program and projects are not completed in a fixed time frame, so public money drained without gain the aim, if government has concern to efficient management of money and resource should give proper attention to administrative management than one election. The BJP and its allied political parties has try to bring a policy of One Nation One Election as a remedies for all sorts of problems which faced by the country is not true in genuine. The nation need to bring the policies of "One nation one Education, One nation one Health, One nation one Employment, One nation one price and One nation one Tax. Let leave the Indian democracy to be vibrant and divergent. Indian democracy wedded with federal structure. Indian democracy sustain with national unity with regional diversity.

Objectives of the Study;

- The study aims to understand the importance of election under the scope of Democracy in Federal structure.
- The study aims to understand the sacred values of election; Representation and participation of diverse people in election.
- This study aims to reveal the political ideology of political party.

Review of Literature;

To make this research article I have to review the various related study materials i.e. journals, articles and online source, in this review of literature I have found that some scholar like Mr Csaba Nikolenyi, a Montreal-based professor at Concordia University studying Indian election has used basic formulate to calculate voter motivation among others, and drew the conclusion that separate election in India were preventing more people participation in the democratic process and his hypothesis is conducting concurrent election that turnout national election percent of vote will rise separate election.

The single election for both parliament and assemblies can suppose to improve the rate of voting percentage but separate election to states and national assembly's hasn't implies to reduce voting rate so it is big things to Indian democracy. The second point that the national law commission of 2018 has suggested that one time election to parliament and assembly's of course it is acceptable in a small countries not in ours, because we had experience of many difficulties in arranging election i.e. management of human resource, supervision and security issues. One election to all body it is challenging task, we need to keep border security and internal order with that there is various threat from anti social and national militant organization. The Election commission also recommended one election but it is political motivated than factual in these consideration one election is not suit to Indian federal democracy and not suppose to try for single election.

Some of the scholars, in favors of continuous election, India were practice that system before and after the independence until 1970s, than after, for various political reasons it has been changed, therefore the same system of election hasn't followed even today. The scholars who in favor of continuous election thought many of the neighbor countries has following one election for its national and province election like in Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal and other countries like Sweden, South Africa, Germany, Spain, Poland and Belgium etc.

- Simultaneous election will decrease the huge expenses of holding separate election. In the 2019 Lok Sabha elections, a whopping Rs 60,000 core (\$8.5 billion) was spent, while the US president and congressional elections coupled were \$ 6.5 billion in 2020.
- NITI Ayog has recommended simultaneous election for parliament and state assemblies in respect of government seek the opinion, it has give in positive response the government.

The constitutional Provision;

The continuous election may go to arrange there will be need of much amendment to constitution i.e. Article 83(2), 85(5)(b) article 172(1),174(2)(b) and more importantly need to amend the people representation act of 1951. In sudden condition no authority can't immediately change the constitution there is need of obtaining confidence of all political parties, people of all caste, religions and communities, it is not feasible without getting consent of people. The major condition of present government there is no 2/3 majority in parliament (both the house of Loksabha and Rajyasabha) in such a condition how can bring the amendment to the constitution of course the ruling government can able to get the majority consent through its power of magic i.e. suspending the opposition party members from the house on various ground and charged the economic and political allegation against the opposition members and ultimately the vary practicing manor of purchasing the members, it's all the ways it would find. For amendment of people representation act there should be need of more than 50% percent of states approval and support it can be easy, because most of the state ruled by BJP led government, these state government have no chance of choice and ratification of bill because they have to accept the direction of their master, it is just serving the interest of his leader than the serving the interest of nation.

In this continuous election proposal, no solution about the Rajyasabha and state councils election, Rajyasabha and states council election would repeating twice or thrice in a year, so it is against to the concept of one election. The important question about contiguous election system, in a general election no political party has not obtain the majority an hung assembly situation created in such a condition any political party not ready to make alliance with other political party in that condition what is the remedy and the other problem is a ruling government lost its confidence it will leads to step down the government, finally other political parties not ready to make coalition with other parties due to

political ideology or other issues ultimately there is no alternative way without going by-election or the house is suspended for until completion its 5 years tenure or next coming general election for avoiding misuse of money. In many of the cases we have an experience of there is no chance to form the government interestingly a situation like 1990s – 2014 is arise what to do. Some of the political events has provide ample examples to us i.e. horse trading, purchasing and hijacking of members these are all the things need to rectify and clarify this ambiguity and more importantly we should think to strengthen the democratic election system into more dynamic, transparent, free from caste, religion and corruption and ultimately keep stronger democracy. The government thought on unwanted expenditure to election, obviously its correct, the government is ready to give up the loan amount of some corporate company as per the congress leader argument the NDA government waiver off 16 lac crore it is big amount compare to election expenditure. In the interest of democracy spending money to election is no misuse if windup all kind of corruption, mismanagement of money we could able carryout many election, election is a energy to sustain democracy.

Research Study;

The study aims to critically evaluate the pros and cons of continuous election system through discussing present and past election of India with comparing elections of other countries. The Indian constitution is undoubtedly an organic constitution and has successfully responded to the changing needs of the nation. India is known as a mother of democracy; living democracy; and largest democracy of the world because of its well wedded working democratic structure, particularly Indian electoral process, democracy and federal structure are reciprocal to each other. The free and fair election held frequently and periodically enhances the spirit of people. Election is heart and soul of Indian democracy. Indian democracy appreciated in the world because of smooth and proper transforming of power to one political party to another political party the party which is win the election, without any confrontation and bloodshed. Indians have respected democracy because they believed in election as a tool and weapons of the people they use this tool and weapons wisely for changing the government which is not works according to the wishes of the people and the ruling government which misuse the power, violate the constitution and rule of law certainly defeat the such government in the next election. The very noble ideas of to world governance is to expanding the decentralization of power with various bodies but one nation one election will curb the spirit of democracy it will leads to autocracy, to prevent autocratic manner of governance our nation maker provide a greater opportunity to people for prevention of antagonistic government to democracy. The idea of one nation one election is uprooting spirit and strength of democracy, Indians were not theatrically understood the concept of democracy but they have legacy of democratic rule and governance were ruled by many regimes like Mourya dynasty, Gupta dynasty and Mysore Princely administration were basis of modern democracy, these systems are collaborative of people participation in decision making and as well as in administration, since from the ancient period because they believed in social and cultural diversity and they obeyed rule of majority opinion likewise Indian modern democracy relied upon general will and wishes of people, based on that our constitution has framed and governance continued since from last 75 years.

The conduct of continuous election to parliament and state assemblies is the reason for all kinds of underdevelopment, misuse of money and engagement of administrative machinery in election development work would not carry accordingly if so, than how can possible to conduct election without use of administrative machinery and money, in continuous election can possible to save the money and resource. The idea of continuous election to parliament and assemblies is a vested interest of a ruling party. The political party which has floated idea of continuous election for all state assemblies and

parliament, why should not able to arrange a one phase election for either parliament or assembly election, parliament election for (house of people) has arranged in different phase, it means India is a big country both in size and population and there is a social, economic and political issues therefore election were conducted in different phase in different states, the election is not a matter of money, time and resource its matter of faith, belief and sanctity of election. Suppose government bring amendment to election will not stand long time because the next upcoming political party may go to change it. The federalism in India lies on maintains national unity with regional diversity. Federalism basis on decentralized power sharing and promoting democratic participation by ensuring representation to different caste, religion and communities, Federalism provides accommodates diversity, federalism promotes regional development, federalism is check and balance, conflict resolution and cooperation between and state and center. If we made amendment to the election these noble principle will spoil. One nation one election is the strategies to divert the minds of people from their due and lapses, since in the last ten years nation has facing several challenges like inflation, unemployment, price hike of food commodities, oil and LPG price, GST for everything, even a person die he has to pay GST for his crimination, don't attempt to divert the issues.

Our ruling government priorities must different instead of bringing ‘‘One Nation One Election’’ should think of regarding bring up the policies of ‘‘One one Education, One nation one Health, One nation one Employment, One nation one Tax and One nation one Price’’. Actually these are the important issues to work on it and it is required to unique and sustainable development of nation than the one election.

Conclusion

In this paper I tried to analyze the subject one nation one election in regard to the present government has try to bring a policy of simultaneous election for parliament and state assemblies at single time in this concern a high level committee has constituted and committee has submitted its report with suggestion for bring up the amendments to simultaneous election. The amendments to one lection is not required the nation need to maintain the present election system i.e. held election at different interval of time means the tenure when expired of house where as to conduct election it is more raise question regarding single election, the union government is going to change of election pattern why should not think over bringing one national education policy and health policy, employment and price policy, these are more essential and helpful to people in getting common and equal opportunity it leads to achieve socio- economic equality and development hence government need to ratify its idea and finally one nation one election is not suit the Indian federal democracy, if government move towards on it will causes more problems than solution so it is an irrelevant issues.

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ELECTION REFORMS IN INDIA: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

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Introduction:

India, the world's largest democracy, holds elections to choose its representatives at multiple levels—Central, State, and Local. While the electoral process is often hailed as a triumph of democratic principles, it has also faced significant challenges that undermine the spirit of democracy. Over the years, several election reforms have been proposed and implemented, but many issues persist. In this article, we will explore the major issues and challenges related to election reforms in India and the ongoing debate surrounding them. India's electoral system, based on the "First-Past-The-Post" (FPTP) system, is primarily governed by the Election Commission of India (ECI) and is structured around a multi-tiered framework, which includes the Central Government (Lok Sabha), State Governments (Vidhan Sabha), and Local Governments (Panchayats and Municipalities). Despite being a robust system that allows for political participation, Indian elections have faced criticism over issues like voter suppression, corruption, criminalization of politics, and the lack of transparency. The Election Commission, a constitutional body, plays a pivotal role in administering and supervising elections. Over the years, several reforms have been introduced to address concerns about the electoral process.

Key Words: Electoral Integrity, Voter Fraud, Electronic Voting Machines (EVMs), Universal Suffrage, VVPAT, Election Commission.

Historical Background of election reforms in India

Election reforms in India have evolved over time to address challenges such as voter participation, fairness, transparency, and the integrity of the electoral process. The Indian electoral system, grounded in the Constitution of 1950, initially followed basic principles of universal suffrage and representation. However, over the years, several issues such as voter fraud, political manipulation, and the misuse of money and muscle power led to the need for reforms. Key milestones include the **recommendations of the Election Commission (EC)**, such as the introduction of **electronic voting machines (EVMs)** in the 1990s to reduce rigging and ensure quicker counting. The **Delimitation Commission** of India periodically reviews and adjusts constituency boundaries to maintain fair representation, often following census data. In the 1990s and early 2000s, reforms such as **compulsory registration of political parties**, **disclosure of election expenses**, and **anti-defection laws** were introduced. The **Model Code of Conduct (MCC)** was developed to regulate political behavior during elections. One of the significant reforms came in **2002**, when the **Representation of the People Act** was amended to ensure the **voting rights of citizens with disabilities**, and **NRI voting** was proposed. Later, the **2010 Election Reforms Committee** recommended further steps, such as enhancing transparency and addressing electoral malpractices. These reforms collectively aimed to make India's elections more credible, inclusive, and transparent.

Issues in Indian Elections

1. Criminalization of Politics

One of the most significant challenges facing Indian elections is the increasing criminalization of politics. According to the Association for Democratic Reforms (ADR), a large number of politicians, especially at the state and national levels, have criminal records. The presence of

candidates with criminal backgrounds on electoral ballots raises concerns about the rule of law, public safety, and governance. In 2021, ADR reported that over 30% of MPs in the Lok Sabha had criminal charges against them. This figure has been steadily rising, despite several Supreme Court directives to prevent individuals with serious criminal charges from contesting elections. While the Representation of the People Act, 1951, disqualifies individuals convicted of certain crimes, there are loopholes in the law that allow criminals to contest and win elections.

2. Money Power and Electoral Corruption

The role of money in elections is another major issue. While election funding is supposed to be regulated under the Representation of the People Act, corruption and black money continue to play a major role in electoral campaigns. Political parties often engage in electoral malpractice through the use of unaccounted funds for bribing voters, media manipulation, and other illegal means. A major reform introduced in 2018, the use of electoral bonds, was meant to bring transparency to political donations. However, the system has been widely criticized for allowing anonymity in political funding, which only perpetuates the influence of unaccounted money in elections.

3. Voter Suppression and Manipulation

Voter suppression, often through fraudulent means, is another challenge in Indian elections. Reports of voter intimidation, bribery, and manipulation of voter rolls have surfaced in several states, particularly in regions with lower literacy rates and high levels of poverty. The use of booth capturing, where election results are tampered with by controlling polling booths, has been prevalent in some parts of the country. The Election Commission has taken steps to address these concerns by introducing the Voter Verified Paper Audit Trail (VVPAT) system and encouraging voter registration drives. However, the challenges of ensuring that every eligible voter can cast their vote without fear or obstruction remain significant.

4. Electronic Voting Machines (EVM) and Voter Trust

The introduction of Electronic Voting Machines (EVMs) was meant to increase efficiency and reduce electoral fraud. However, these machines have been at the centre of controversy over the years. Accusations of tampering and hacking of EVMs have been raised by political parties, particularly after contentious elections. While the Election Commission has maintained that EVMs are secure and tamper-proof, the lack of widespread trust in the technology continues to be an issue. Several political leaders have called for a return to paper ballots, arguing that the electronic system is prone to manipulation. In response, the Election Commission has introduced measures like VVPAT to ensure greater transparency, but scepticism persists, especially in light of some reported glitches and errors in the functioning of EVMs during high-profile elections.

5. Voter Identification and Registration

Voter identification and registration have been areas of concern in India, especially considering the country's large and diverse population. The process of voter registration is often marred by bureaucratic inefficiencies, data errors, and lack of awareness, which result in eligible voters being left out of the rolls or incorrectly classified. The introduction of the Electors Photo Identity Card (EPIC) and the National Voters' Service Portal (NVSP) was aimed at addressing these issues. However, in some areas, particularly in rural and remote parts of the country, large segments of the population, including women and minorities, still face challenges in registering to vote.

6. Polarization and Voter Identity

Electoral polarization has emerged as a growing concern in India. Political parties often use identity-based politics—appealing to voters based on religion, caste, or region—to secure electoral victories. This exacerbates social divisions and undermines the principle of an inclusive democracy. Voter loyalty to parties based on caste or religious identity often leads to a lack of policy debates and ideological discussions, focusing instead on creating social divides for political gain. This issue is particularly prevalent in states like Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, and West Bengal, where identity-based politics has shaped the outcomes of elections. The challenge is to encourage voters to choose representatives based on policies and governance rather than on parochial factors.

7. Electoral Violence and Malpractices

Electoral violence, though not as widespread as it was in the past, remains a concern in some states, particularly in regions like West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, and Bihar. Instances of political violence during elections often lead to deaths, injuries, and property damage, undermining the legitimacy of the electoral process. In many cases, local political bosses or criminal elements exert influence over elections, intimidating voters and even candidates. The central and state governments have been criticized for not doing enough to curb electoral violence. Although the Election Commission has taken action, deploying paramilitary forces and setting up monitoring systems, the challenge of preventing violence in certain areas continues to be a concern.

Challenges in Election Reforms

1. Lack of Political Will

One of the primary obstacles to comprehensive election reforms in India is the lack of political will. Political parties, especially those in power, often resist reforms that may diminish their electoral prospects. For instance, a political party benefiting from the status quo is unlikely to push for transparency in funding or the disqualification of criminal candidates. In some cases, parties themselves have been accused of engaging in corrupt practices like bribing voters or using muscle power. Therefore, there is a reluctance to introduce reforms that might harm their immediate electoral interests.

2. Institutional Weakness

Although the Election Commission is an independent body, it often faces challenges in enforcing election laws effectively. With limited resources and manpower, the Commission is sometimes unable to fully address the various malpractices occurring during elections. Furthermore, enforcement of laws related to campaign finance and voter rights is often weak, leading to widespread violations. There is also a lack of effective coordination between state election commissions and the Election Commission of India, especially during elections in multiple states. This makes it difficult to ensure consistency and fairness across all electoral constituencies.

3. Lack of Electoral Awareness

Voter awareness is another key challenge in ensuring the effectiveness of election reforms. Many voters, especially in rural areas, are not fully aware of their rights or the electoral process. Lack of awareness about the importance of voting, the functioning of political parties, and the significance of electoral reforms hinders the success of many reform initiatives. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs), civil society groups, and the Election Commission itself

have made efforts to increase voter literacy, but challenges persist in reaching marginalized communities, especially those in tribal areas and backward regions.

4. Technological Barriers

While technology has played a key role in modernizing India's electoral system, issues like internet connectivity, particularly in remote and rural areas, can hinder the efficient conduct of elections. Moreover, despite advances in electronic voting and the introduction of VVPATs, the distrust in technology remains a significant barrier. The Election Commission must continue to work on improving the technological infrastructure to ensure more transparency and voter confidence.

Conclusion

Election reforms in India are essential for the continued functioning of the world's largest democracy. While significant strides have been made in addressing some issues, such as the introduction of VVPATs, online voter registration, and restrictions on criminal candidates, a host of challenges remain. Political will, institutional strengthening, voter education, and technological advancements will be key to implementing comprehensive reforms that ensure a free, fair, and transparent electoral process. As India heads toward future elections, the need for a robust electoral system that upholds the values of democracy becomes even more urgent. The success of electoral reforms will depend on the collective efforts of political parties, the Election Commission, civil society, and voters themselves.

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LOCKE'S LIBERTY, EQUALITY, POPULAR SOVEREIGNTY AND CHRISTIAN THEOLOGY

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Abstract

Popular sovereignty, equality, and liberty are some of the fundamental tenets of democracy. These are the essential ideas that democracy needs to be established and advanced. Through his well-known work "Two Treatises of the Civil Government," John Locke, one of the social contractual theorists, aims to construct limited government. He is considered the "father of liberalism" because of his ideas on equality, liberty, and popular sovereignty. He rejects the Bible-based arguments of Robert Filmer's notion of absolute monarchy in his treatise. John Locke critiques the Filmer's claims using the same Bible, but with a different interpretation. The Bible served as the primary basis of argument for both John Locke and Robert Filmer. Hence the thoughts of both these thinkers are influenced by Christian theology. Locke's beliefs in relation with, Liberty, Equality and Popular sovereignty are not exempted from the effect of the theology, instead Bible is the one and only source of his entire thoughts. This article highlights these influences and demonstrates how John Locke's views on liberty, equality, and popular sovereignty are solely grounded in Christian theology.

Keywords: *Liberty, Equality, Popular sovereignty, John Locke, Robert Filmer and Christian theology*

Introduction:

Robert Filmer was a great advocate of absolute monarchy. John Locke refuted Filmer's ideas in his well-known work "Two Treatises of Government." Filmer's renowned book "Patriarcha," published in 1680, reflects his views on absolute monarchy. Using the royal authority, the subordination of Eve, and fatherhood, he attempted to establish absolute monarchy based on biblical verses. John Locke countered each of Filmer's arguments and laid the foundation for the concepts of liberty, equality, and popular sovereignty on the basis of interpretation of Biblical verses. Hence, Locke's concepts have strong theological foundations.

Sovereignty of Adam by Royal Authority

Filmer's defense of the absolute monarchy is based in part on the following claims: Princes are absolute monarchs, slaves lack the right of consent, Adam was the first absolute monarch, and all subsequent princes have been so since. Filmer argues, "Men are not born free, and therefore could never have the liberty to choose either governors, or forms of government." He invokes royal authority (the right of fatherhood) to support his claim that men are born in subjection to their parents and are therefore not free. He invokes the decalogue's admonition to "honor your father" in order to affirm his inherent claim to royal authority. In light of this, he offers his own interpretation of the Bible verses that Kings, by right of parents, have supreme jurisdiction; the superiority of the princes is above the laws; the father of the family governs no other law but by his own will; Adam and his successors have royal authority over their children; Adam and the patriarchs have absolute power of life and death; and kingly power is granted by the law of God, so no lesser law can limit it. The reason why monarchs enact laws is because they are too busy with wars and public affairs, to listen to the desires and wills of the kings' laws are created. In the table of laws, each private individual can discover the king's will. In the opinion

of Filmer, the son, the subject, and the servant or slave are all one and the same; Adam was the father, the king, and the lord of his family. The parent has the authority to sell or give away his servants or children. According to his interpretation of the Bible, a man-servant and a made-servant are among the owner's belongings and commodities. The subjects were denied their freedom, rights, not even the right to life.

Political Power is different from Right of Fatherhood

Locke refutes the Filmer's argument above. The first criticism is that Filmer did not offer any evidence to support the Adam's royal authority. The sole basis for Filmer's whole argument is the Decalogue's fifth mandate, "honor thy father." Filmer has ill termed this commandment, according to Locke. Locke questions why cannot one argue that by using the next half of the commandment, "Honour thy mother", that all powers were originally in the mother? In this sense, Locke contends that the authority of the parent and political power are not the same. The Decalogue's fifth commandment relates to the father's authority but not to governmental power. Adam will therefore not be regarded as king. Furthermore, the number of sovereigns is equal to the number of fathers if a father is a sovereign by virtue of his paternal rights. Then, a single sovereign is not possible.

Sovereignty of Adam by subordination of Eve

Using Genesis iii.16, "Your desire shall be to thy husband, and he shall rule over thee," Robert Filmer asserts that Eve is subservient to Adam. God chastised Adam and Eve for breaking their pact with him and forced Eve to pay attention to what her husband had to say. Adam was given authority over Eve. She was the first to disobey, and Adam came after her.

God cursed both, according to Locke's counterargument. It is impossible to believe that God gave Adam rights and benefits, as well as authority and dignity. He was degraded since he shared in the sin. Locke chastises the Gall for giving Adam all the benefits and unlimited power while also making him a day laborer and monarch, throwing him "Paradise till the ground." As stated in verse 19, "In the sweat of thy face thou shalt eat thy bread," God created Adam to be a laborer rather than a monarch. For as long as Adam lived, not just temporarily.

Locke further argues that Filmer used the following verse to indicate the monarchical government of Adam including Eve: "Unto the woman he said, I will greatly multiply thy sorrow and thy conception; in sorrow thou shalt bring forth children, and thy desire shall be to thy husband, and he shall rule over thee." Locke opines that these words are not saying anything about Adam. Moreover, this verse is related to conjugal relationship, but not to political. It cannot be treated as original grant of the government and foundation of monarchical rule. Locke mentioned another verse, "that the elder should serve the younger", Gen. xxv. 23, to denounce the interpretation of the Filmer's. this verse related to Jacob and Esau. As Jacob is the younger and Esau is the elder one cannot suppose here that Jacob is Esau's Sovereign.

Sovereignty of Adam by Fatherhood

The Filmer also invoked Adam's paternity as justification for his absolute reign. "Not only did Adam have royal authority over his children by virtue of his fatherhood, but so did the subsequent patriarchs," the Filmer claims. By birth, every man becomes a subject of the one who bears him. No one has ever been born free because Adam was the sole man created and all others have been begotten thereafter.

Locke do not agree with the Filmer's Fatherhood argument. Locke says, "begetting of children makes them not slaves to their fathers". Filmer and others failed to remember that "God, who is the author and giver of life: it is in him alone we live, move, and have our being". Locke questions how

one can say that he will be the giver of life, where the philosophers, anatomists, in spite of the diligent effort to trace the source of life. How can one impose himself the incomprehensible work of the Almighty. Locke also cites Biblical verses, "God our maker," and "the Lord our maker" to prove his view point that God, not biological father, is the ultimate creator of the man. He also stresses the role of the mother in begetting a child. She has also equal authority over her child. Locke also mentions the revelation of the God in the Scripture that "his father and his mother that begot him", Deut. xxi. 16. "Cursed be he that setteth light by his father or his mother." "In thee have they set light by father and mother", Ezeki. xxii. 7. "Children, obey your parents;" in some places it neglects even the priority of order, which is thought due to the father, and the mother is put first, as Lev. xix.

Parental Power and its limitations

According to Locke, Parental power does not exist for long. At the age of 21, both father and children are free equally. After nonage, both are subject to same law without any dominion over the life, liberty and estate of the son by the father. The power of the command of the father ends with the nonage. God has placed rationality in every human being. Hence, he is free and equal with each other.

Locke's views on Slavery

Liberty, according to the Locke, is free from any supreme power on the earth. He should be not under any authority or will of the man. Freedom is no restrictions other than the law of nature. Locke does not agree with the Filmer's view on freedom: "A liberty for everyone to do what he lists, to live as he pleases, and not to be tied by any laws". Man can be restricted only by the commonwealth formed on the basis of his consent.

Conclusion

Filmer has proposed his theory of absolute monarchy on the basis of Christian theology enshrined in the Bible. Locke too countered Filmer with the same. Locke's concepts of liberty, equality and sovereignty of the people are entirely based upon the Christian theology.

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UNDERSTANDING THE CONTEMPORARY FOREIGN POLICY OF INDIA FROM THE IDEOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK DECOLONIALITY

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Keywords: *Decoloniality, Multipolarity, Cultural Diplomacy, multilateralism, Jaishankar Doctrine.*

Introduction:

India's foreign policy has undergone significant strategic changes and paradigm shifts in the past decade. When Narendra Modi took office in 2014, India's foreign policy experienced a significant Ideological shift. One of the visible major shifts was India's foreign and strategic policy approach. Political analysts and intellectuals opine that Indian polity underwent a rightward turn, and the dawn of a neo-nationalist establishment brought the issues of nationalism and national security onto the centre stage. However, one of the most significant changes brought about by the Modi government was the push towards India's cultural strength and an assertive portrayal of India's incredible history, heritage, and civilizational ethos on the world stage. This approach indicated the rise of the decoloniality framework and a conscious policy shift from the earlier postcolonial framework. Therefore, we must thematically approach the ideological framework of decoloniality and understand the genesis of the shift from postcolonialism. The postcolonial approach to India's foreign policy was formulated mainly in the early years of India's Independence under the leadership of Jawaharlal Nehru and focused on how India as a postcolonial country would foster international relations. The main aim was to ensure political and institutional freedom from the colonizer and lay the genesis of a new nation based on mutual respect and peaceful co-existence of the world. In those times, another major objective was to stay non-aligned with the ideological camps of capitalism led by the USA and Socialism led by the USSR. However, the era of unipolarity began with the end of the Cold War in the 1990s and the emergence of the USA as the sole global hegemon. With the US's unfettered domination over the geostrategic framework from the early 1990s to 2010, the era of unilateralism prospered in the world order. From 2010 onwards, we have witnessed the growth of China as a world power, which is now considered the second most powerful country in the world in terms of brut hard power dynamics. But India, too, has been dominating the global discourse for the last two decades and has emerged as a significant power in the world. Therefore, India needs to relook at and systematically recalibrate its foreign policy strategy. To achieve this objective, the ideological tool of decoloniality is playing a vital role in rekindling the thought process of India's political and strategic community. Through this thematic paper, we will understand how a few foreign policy measures of the last decade have brought about certain strategic shifts through the lens of decoloniality.

Understanding the meanings of doctrine and decoloniality and the difference from post-colonialism:

In international relations, a doctrine refers to a set of ideas, ideologies, principles, and policy frameworks used as strategies, tactics, and practices to guide one's actions in pursuing and realising the intended objectives. Simply put, doctrine involves a combination of art, science, and wisdom to realize the goals.

Decoloniality is a rational psyche, ontology and the matrix of power structure generated by the systemic processes in the aftermath of colonization and settler colonialism. It aims to do away with the colonial

interpretations of native societies and cultures and free the native community from the colonial lens and gaze from both the psychological and intellectual angles, which is referred to as the decolonization of the mind. Unlike post-colonialism, which provides a critique of colonial structures and institutions, decoloniality aids in breaking away from the collective colonial consciousness. Decoloniality is an academic movement and worldview that seeks to eradicate the colonial power structures that continue to exist long after formal colonialism has ceased. With its origins in the viewpoints of scholars from the Global South and Latin America, decoloniality challenges the hegemony of Eurocentric intellectual, cultural, and political systems that have historically ignored alternative ways of knowing and being. It encourages the revival of Indigenous perspectives and colonially oppressed populations' empowerment and cultural revitalization. Decoloniality emphasises local knowledge and experiences and aims to eliminate power imbalances and advance a more equitable global order. Ultimately, it encourages the growth of regions free from colonial rule where many voices can flourish, redefining identity, knowledge, and sovereignty.

Postcolonialism and decolonisation are two different but related ideas that deal with colonial legacies. The study of colonialism's cultural, political, and social effects, with an emphasis on how former colonies deal with identity and power after gaining independence, is known as post-colonialism. It examines hybrid identities in post-independence societies and challenges Eurocentric narratives, frequently in sociology, history, and literature. In contrast, decoloniality strongly emphasises destroying colonial power systems that still exist in governance, culture, and knowledge. It opposes the dominance of Western modernity and promotes alternative epistemologies rooted in viewpoints from the Global South. Decoloniality actively works to destroy and replace colonial frameworks, providing a continuous, useful strategy for freedom beyond independence, while postcolonialism considers the impacts of colonialism.

Understanding Cultural Diplomacy in India's Context and its interlinkages with Decoloniality:

Cultural Diplomacy can be described as a course of actions which are based on the utilization and exchange of ideas, values, traditions and other aspects of culture or identity, whether to strengthen relationships, enhance socio-cultural cooperation, promote national interests and beyond; Cultural diplomacy is an essential aspect of a nation's soft power. The global impact of India's soft power was felt long before the term found place in popular parlance in the 21st century. The quest for Indian arts, culture and spiritualism has attracted people worldwide for several centuries now. PM Modi has reoriented Indian diplomacy by combining it with the new elements of soft power. PM Modi came up with the Paanchajanya framework, a contrarian foreign policy framework similar to the Nehruvian Panchasheel policy.

It consists of five pillars of soft power.

They are;

- 1) Samman (dignity),
- 2) Samvaad (dialogue),
- 3) Samridhhi (shared prosperity),
- 4) Suruksha (regional and global security),
- 5) Sanskriti Evam Sabhayata (Cultural and civilizational links).

With this framework of Paanchajanya, inspired by Chanakya's Doctrine of Mandala, the Prime Minister has showcased his ambition to elevate India's status as an emerging global power. This framework places India's national interest and national security as of prime importance while developing mutual respect and dignity towards India. In his convocation address at Banaras Hindu University in 2016, he

affirmed the view, “In the present age, which can be considered an era of knowledge, our roles and responsibilities have increased. We must emerge as a Vishwa guru, not only to provide a new direction to the world but also to protect our heritage”. The content of cultural exports from India has been a fine blend of the modern cultural values of the world with ancient traditional values of India (such as yoga, dharmic values, traditional medicine, etc.) to create a strong ‘Brand India’ on a global scale. These are interlinked with India’s broader geopolitical and geoeconomic goals. These goals mainly reflect how India has changed its views and approach of foreign policy which is oriented towards decoloniality. The revocation of Chanakya's cultural and civilisational ethos demonstrates that India is attempting to move away from the Western and Eurocentric world views and proudly endorse the Indian epistemology towards its knowledge generation, especially in the cultural sphere, through the active promotion of cultural diplomacy.

Jaishankar Doctrine in Foreign policy, a testimony towards decoloniality:

Dr Jaishankar appears to be following the decoloniality approach to confront the Western hegemony. He has stressed India's historical, cultural, and civilizational significance by reinvigorating its civilizational consciousness and cultural pride. He cited the example of India’s vaccine diplomacy as a benevolent gesture of promoting human values, thereby indicating the eternal Indic values of integral humanism. By doing so, he has directly challenged the predominance of Western universalism on the cultural, economic and political front. Let us examine the few features of Jaishankar's Doctrine, which involves decoloniality approach towards foreign policy.

Flagging the arrogance of American Hegemony and Neo-colonialism of the West:

Dr Jaishankar has never shied away from publicly demonstrating his discontent with the American sinister geopolitical games of oppressing and changing regimes across the world, which caters to its self-interests at best. He openly called out their freedom, liberty and democracy trilogy to be self-serving goals for a larger geopolitical footprint and domination. According to him, the American state and their economic powerhouse, fuelled by its military-industrial complex, is just an attempt to re-colonize the world with its hegemonistic tendencies to make the other countries subservient in the vicious cycles of dependency, as it is clearly a part of their strategic game-plan. Dr Jaishankar has also criticized the USA's and European nations' aggressive diplomacy and cultural superiority when they engage with the third world. American hegemony, according to Dr S Jaishankar, is arrogant and, therefore, needs to be given a cultural and civilisational response by asserting the civilisational pride of India through its foreign policy measures and, therefore, threading the path of decoloniality.

Encouraging the growth of minilateral groupings;

Minilateral groupings, which involve three to four or a maximum of five countries, are becoming very popular and gaining geopolitical traction at present. The Quad grouping is a classic example of this. The other emerging grouping of partnerships between India, UAE, Israel and the USA, popularly described as the Middle Eastern quad, is yet another example of the growing multilateralism in the world. The intellectual brain behind the forging of these multilateral partnerships happens to be Dr Jaishankar. As per his calculation and strategy, small, issue-based, channelised, goal-oriented minilaterals can overcome the failures and shortcomings of large traditional international organizations and west-driven multilateral forums like G20. Dr Jaishankar believes that Minilaterals are strategically a viable option to engage for countries like India mainly because the traditional international institutions not just geopolitically dominate the decision-making but also impose their inherent values and ethos of Western civilizations, which might not be universally applicable. By promoting the Minilaterals, which are region and issue-specific, the countries can limit not just the political impact of the West but also

garner and accommodate region-specific values, interests and cultural aspects of their national identity. The groupings and regroupings of minilaterals mainly reduce the Eurocentric Western values and organisational frameworks that traditional international institutions are dominated by, thereby adopting the core principles of decoloniality.

Envisioning a multialigned and multipolar world order;

Dr Jaishankar believes that a multi-aligned world, with diversified partnerships based on economy, trade and commerce, security, geo-strategic necessity, and counter-balancing the adversaries with different countries based on the cost-benefit analysis, needs to be carried out by each country. This, in a way, justifies the Chanakyan principle that “there are no permanent friends or enemies in the world”. In fact, Dr Jaishankar has indicated in several instances that “there are permanent interests, neither friends nor enemies”; this is the real-politick of malalignment, in Jaishankar’s lens. He has envisaged the need for a multipolar world where the geopolitical power dynamics are not operated by one country, a set of countries or ideological power blocks as it happened in the Cold War. Although a new cold war has begun, with the rise of Chinese hegemony, Dr Jaishankar’s advocacy of multipolarity has become more assertive. In his view, diverse, plural, and collective participation in global affairs would churn out more just and favourable conditions for each and every country to satisfy its individual goals and objectives. Though this approach might not solve all longstanding strategic issues, it would facilitate smoother functioning in international affairs. But this approach does not garner the cultural and racial superiority that the bipolar world under the USA and USSR had or the Unipolar World under the USA. There was a cultural and racial superiority and domination of the white race that emanated all through the USA, Western Europe and the USSR. It kept the third world out of the power structure not merely because of its inferior economic or military capabilities but also because of a clear racial and cultural inferiority. Therefore, Dr Jaishankar’s advocacy for multipolarity and multi-alignment can be seen as a progressive attempt, through the decoloniality framework, to bridge the racial and cultural divide that the previously existing world order had created.

Conclusion:

Decoloniality is a rational psyche, ontology and the matrix of power structure generated by the systemic processes in the aftermath of colonization and settler colonialism. It aims to do away with the colonial interpretations of native societies and cultures and free the native community from the colonial lens and gaze from both the psychological and intellectual angles, which is called the decolonization of the mind. Unlike post-colonialism, which provides a critique of colonial structures and institutions, decoloniality aids in breaking away from the collective colonial consciousness. In conclusion, the paradigm shift of the foreign policy of the Modi government, based on the Jaishankar Doctrine, signifies a significant move away from colonialism and towards decolonisation. It strongly emphasises India's global identity, cultural pride, and civilisational ethos. India reinterprets its strategic objectives using Indigenous frameworks and a decolonial lens by opposing Western hegemony, advancing minilateral alliances, and arguing for a multipolar world. In addition to strengthening India's geopolitical position, this paradigm promotes a world order based on justice and respect for one another. India establishes itself as a thought leader in creating a fair and inclusive global order by fusing cultural diplomacy with geopolitical goals.

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ELECTION COMMISSION OF INDIA: MALA FIDE OR MERELY INCOMPETENT?**Prof. B. H Satyanarayana***DOS in Political Science, Sahyadri Arts College Vidyanagar, Shivamogga**Email: bhsatyanarayana@gmail.com Mob: 9740799309*

Abstract

Elections that are free and fair are essential to democracy. People may demonstrate their trust in the government and acknowledge the power of giving the government's authority legitimacy through elections. One of the indicators of democracy is elections. Even though India has the biggest democracy in the world, we believe that it isn't functioning well for a number of reasons. Free and fair elections are said to be protected by the Election Commission of India. To strengthen democracy and improve election fairness, the Election Commission has carried out a number of commendable electoral reforms.

This essay outlines the Election Commission of India's role in implementing reforms and the steps it has taken to prevent misconduct. "The election commission is dealing with a number of issues, including the dominance of force and money power, criminalization of politics, election financing that goes beyond the law, booth capturing, voter intimidation, voter buying, tampered electoral rolls, widespread election rigging, and the misuse of caste and religion in voter registration. The election commission's contribution to India's post-independence electoral reforms is assessed in this study. "Free and fair elections held on a periodic basis based on the adult franchise are the foundation of the parliamentary system, while social and economic democracy may require much more."

Key words: *Neutrality and Integrity, Public Interest Litigation, Moral Code of Conduct, Use of Social Media, Allurement of ECI.*

Does it need Transformation?

India is preparing for its largest celebration, the 17th Lok Sabha elections in 2019, which will be the largest democracy in the world. The independence, impartiality, and integrity of India's statutory and constitutional authorities are the cornerstones of its democracy. Every five years, India has elections to uphold and defend its democracy. These elections always turn into a huge celebration that unites people from all walks of life, including castes, colors, languages, and faiths.

India's democracy is distinct from other democracies throughout the world because diversity is accepted as the rule rather than the exception. It has its own set of difficulties and complications. In the constantly shifting dynamics of Indian elections, it calls for an organization that can withstand pressure and provide innovative answers and fast corrections.

Role of Election Commission of India

The Election Commission is responsible for overseeing the fair and transparent conduct of elections in India. It is undoubtedly among the most valuable establishments. an organization tasked with choosing the country's future leader and preserving democracy among its citizens.

The Indian Constitution's Article 324 grants the Election Commission of India the authority to oversee, manage, and guide the whole electoral process for the legislature (State Legislative Assembly and State Legislative Council), the president and vice president of India, and the parliament.

From the outset, the EC's work begins. By starting the enrollment procedure, EC starts the election. With billions of people living in India, it is an enormous undertaking. The variety and demographic shifts make it much more difficult and time-consuming. In addition to granting everyone the right to vote, EC also makes sure that everyone has access to it. Only with strong infrastructure and challenging terrain can it succeed. Innovative solutions are used to tackle security concerns. EC makes certain that all of these challenges are overcome.

The EC's next task is to make sure the nation's election process is proceeding smoothly. Only when the rules and regulations that are implemented are appropriately overseen will it be feasible. In order for election outcomes to accurately represent people's desires, the EC's role is to ensure that everyone is treated equally.

Therefore, maintaining the institution's quality is crucial to ensuring that its legitimacy and accountability are never questioned". EC ought to be the untouchable institution whose integrity is unquestionable and whose reliability is always highly valued.

Why EC needs a makeover?

The validity and dependability of EC have been questioned recently. Many political parties and commentators have questioned whether the EC is acting in an unbiased and fair manner. Its legally mandated role as an agent guarantees the integrity of the electoral process. However, recent events have raised questions about whether EC is an impartial and fair body or if it has become into a tool of the ruling party.

Numerous new media have emerged in this era of digital growth, presenting EC with new difficulties. The founding assembly, which had not anticipated such problems, created the EC's functions and rules. Existing candidates and political parties devise new ways to get around each new regulation. Appointment, partisanship, bought news, voting bribery, and hate speech issues have gained prominence. EC must therefore always be alert to develop new opportunities and solutions.

Let's examine some of the problems that EC is facing.

Independence and political Influence

The Supreme Court's Constitution Bench is considering a public interest lawsuit (PIL) that aims to fortify the Indian Election Commission (ECI). "It contains a suggestion to establish a separate system for choosing the Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) and Election Commissioners (ECs), who are now chosen at random by the president of the day without any set standards or procedures.

It has occasionally seemed as though EC is supporting the political parties (either in relaxation of Moral Code of Conduct or calling up of election dates as seen during Gujarat assembly elections). This is a risky tendency that can cast doubt on EC's independence and dependability.

It is necessary to create a structured guideline outlining the standards for choosing and eliminating ECs and CECs. It should ensure that its ideals and work ethics are not questioned.

Election Expenditure

The 2024 Lok Sabha Election is poised to shatter previous records and become the most expensive electoral event in the world. According to the Centre for Media Studies, the cost of a single vote in India has now reached an astonishing Rs. 1,400. Political parties across the spectrum, from the ruling BJP to the opposition Congress and Samajwadi Party, are sparing no expense to win over voters. Estimates suggest that approximately Rs 1 lakh crore was spent this election, marking a significant jump from the Rs. 55,000-60,000 crore spent in the 2019 elections. The total estimated expenditure for the 2024 elections reached a staggering Rs 1.35 lakh crore. This surpasses the spending in the 2020 US elections, which stood at Rs 1.2 lakh crore.

A cap on election money has been imposed by the EC for both candidates and parties. However, in an attempt to win over votes, regulations have been broken. Black money and voter bribery cases have made headlines. The EC has not stopped the flow of illicit funds. Even if electoral bonds are being promoted as a solution to stop the misuse of unaccountable funds, the European Commission ought to think of alternative creative ways to stop this problem.

Criminalization of Politics

The number of candidates with criminal histories has increased in the most recent Lok Sabha elections. Money and physical strength are being deployed to their fullest potential as political parties compete for seats. To stop the criminalization of politics, the EC turned to the Supreme Court for assistance. In its ruling on the criminalization of politics, a five-judge Supreme Court bench asked the court to exclude politicians who are accused of serious crimes including rape, abduction, and murder from running for office.

Candidates must also disclose their income, educational background, criminal history, and any outstanding cases. While it is a start in the right direction, it takes a while for EC to conduct thorough checks to confirm the applicants' details. Candidates spread misleading information as a result of this inaction.

Paid News

Paid news presents ECI with its next major obstacle. It is now a serious threat to EC. Reports have verified the authenticity of sponsored news in several cases. Since the news is already in the public domain, the difficulty is in controlling it.

Although the EC has previously disciplined candidates by taking action against them, the fact that it is still widespread demonstrates how candidates are taking advantage of EC's own weaknesses. Due to a lack of records and circumstantial evidence, it is now challenging to prove that a news item is paid, even if it is. Because of the way that false news has been promoted as a result of media and government leaders working together, it is getting harder for EC to tell the difference between fake and true news.

Use of Social Media

Social media is a dynamic medium. It gives us a way to spread misinformation and information more quickly. With the growing usage of mobile and internet technologies, social media's effect has increased. Therefore, it makes sense for political leaders to use this platform for their campaigning. This platform's scope and depth are so extensive that EC is having trouble managing the amount of information. Every single advertising word or film cannot be controlled.

EC has a monitoring committee to keep an eye out for political advertisements in print and electronic media that might undermine society or violate moral standards. Voters' or other vigilantes' concerns are the social media committee's primary source of information. Given the extensive and limitless reach of social media, EC ought to consider multi-stakeholder engagement. It should establish new rules to clear up any confusion about what may and cannot be spread.

EVM and VVPAT

Elections for legislative assemblies in many Indian states had previously been questioned after allegations that they were rigged or controlled. The opposition parties have protested that the results were favoring the ruling party and that the electronic voting machine (EVM) was being digitally heckled. EC has finally decided to utilize VVPAT in these elections after several attempts to deny these charges.

Sending a favorable message to the public about the free and fair nature of Indian elections is crucial. Since EC is a constitutional body, it should not participate in election tampering. However, EC's failure to persuade the masses promptly has left a mark, and its reputation has already suffered. The watchdog has difficulties since the EVM tampering debate is still ongoing and voter skepticism persists.

Allurement of ECI

EC has evolved into a reputable and accountable organization throughout time. Its ability to maintain its principles and ideals is evidence of this. As individuals and society have evolved, EC has adjusted its methods of operation. It has given us a variety of suggestions and ideas to control the political parties. There is no room for disagreement on EC's neutrality and work ethics. However, it is EC's responsibility to continue operating with impartiality, efficiency, and honesty”.

EC has evolved into a reputable and accountable organization throughout time. Its ability to maintain its principles and ideals is evidence of this. As individuals and society have evolved, EC has adjusted its methods of operation. It has given us a variety of suggestions and ideas to control the political parties. There is no room for disagreement on EC's neutrality and work ethics. However, it is EC's responsibility to continue operating with impartiality, efficiency, and honesty.

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THE ROLE OF LITERATURE IN CULTURAL DIVERSITY AND NATIONAL UNITY**Dr. Nanjundaiah D.**

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Abstract

¹This article explores the dual role of literature in promoting cultural diversity and fostering national unity, emphasizing its importance in multicultural societies. Literature, as a form of storytelling and artistic expression, captures the unique traditions, values, languages, and histories of diverse communities, thereby preserving cultural heritage and enriching social identity. At the same time, literature fosters empathy and understanding by exposing readers to perspectives and experiences beyond their own, helping to bridge cultural divides. Through narratives that reflect universal human values—such as resilience, justice, and compassion—literature reveals commonalities across different communities, contributing to a sense of shared purpose and identity.

The article investigates literature's unifying role in constructing national identity by providing shared narratives that citizens of all backgrounds can connect with, ultimately creating a collective sense of belonging. It also highlights literature's potential as an agent of social change, as authors often challenge societal inequalities and advocate for inclusion and justice through their works. This impact is further examined through case studies of national literature from various multicultural societies, illustrating how literature can simultaneously celebrate diversity and build unity.

Methodologically, the article utilizes a literature review, textual analysis, case studies, and comparative analysis to assess the literature's role in preserving diversity and promoting unity. Findings indicate that literature not only captures cultural specificity but also contributes to an inclusive national identity that values all cultural expressions. As such, literature is a powerful force in building cohesive societies that respect and learn from their diversity. By examining literature's contributions to cultural preservation, empathy, and unity, the article underscores its enduring significance in shaping national identity in a globalized world.

Keywords: Cultural diversity, national unity, literature, empathy, identity

Introduction:

In an increasingly interconnected world, the interplay between cultural diversity and national unity has become a significant focal point in societies worldwide. Literature, as a powerful medium of expression and communication, plays a pivotal role in this dynamic. Through stories, poetry, folklore, and historical narratives, literature² captures the essence of diverse cultural identities while simultaneously serving as a common ground that can unite people within a nation. It bridges cultural divides by providing readers with a window into the lives, traditions, and values of others, promoting empathy and understanding across different social and ethnic groups.

At its core, literature not only preserves and celebrates the unique aspects of each culture but also promotes cohesion by crafting shared narratives that contribute to a national identity. This dual capacity—to highlight both distinctiveness and commonality—places literature at the heart of building inclusive and harmonious societies. The impact of literature in multicultural contexts is profound, as it offers insights into the lived experiences of various communities, challenges stereotypes, and

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² Literature

encourages respect for cultural plurality. Simultaneously, it reminds readers of the universal human values that transcend cultural differences, fostering a sense of collective belonging and unity.

In a time marked by both cultural resurgence and societal division, understanding literature's role in nurturing cultural diversity and national unity is more relevant than ever. This article explores how literature preserves cultural heritage, fosters empathy, and bridges differences, ultimately underscoring its essential role in constructing a cohesive yet diverse society. Through examining the multifaceted contributions of literature, we gain a deeper appreciation for how it shapes a nation's identity, connects its people, and paves the way for a more inclusive future.

Review of Literature: The Role of Literature in Cultural Diversity and National Unity

1. Preservation of Cultural Heritage

Studies highlight literature's role³ in capturing and preserving cultural traditions, languages, and historical narratives, which are vital for maintaining cultural heritage. Literature acts as an archive of cultural values, especially in societies where oral traditions are predominant. Researchers emphasize that by documenting these unique stories, literature prevents the erosion of cultural identities in the face of globalization.

2. Promotion of Empathy and Cross-Cultural Understanding

Scholars widely agree on literature's capacity to cultivate empathy by allowing readers to experience life from diverse perspectives. Literary critics argue that by engaging with characters from different cultural backgrounds, readers gain insight into values and beliefs that differ from their own, reducing prejudices and fostering cross-cultural understanding.

3. Literature as a Unifying Force in National Identity

Research shows that literature plays a unifying role by contributing to a shared national identity, especially in multicultural societies. Texts that reflect collective histories or shared experiences create a common ground for people across diverse backgrounds. Academics note that national literature can create a sense of belonging and pride by emphasizing commonalities among citizens while still respecting their diversity.

4. Social Change and Inclusivity

Literature is recognized for its potential to drive social change by highlighting issues of inequality, marginalization, and injustice. Many studies discuss how authors use their work to advocate for the rights of underrepresented communities, encouraging readers to reflect on and address social disparities. Literature thus serves as a tool for inclusion, encouraging societies to embrace and integrate all voices.

5. Educational Role in Cultural Awareness

Literature is frequently highlighted as an educational resource for promoting cultural awareness and respect among young readers. Research in educational psychology points out that by incorporating diverse literary works into school curricula, students are exposed to multiple perspectives and cultures from a young age. This exposure builds open-mindedness, reduces cultural biases, and instills respect for diversity, laying the groundwork for a more inclusive society.

Methodology: The Role of Literature in Cultural Diversity and National Unity

1. Literature Review

A comprehensive review of existing literature on cultural diversity, national unity, and the role of literature in promoting both was conducted. This included analyzing scholarly articles, books, and case

³ Role

studies to understand the theoretical framework and previous findings in this area. Key themes were identified to frame the article's main arguments.

2. Textual Analysis

Representative literary works from diverse cultural backgrounds were analyzed to examine how they capture cultural traditions and promote unity. Texts such as novels, poems, and folk tales that highlight various cultural experiences were selected to illustrate literature's role in preserving cultural identity and fostering shared values.

3. Case Studies of National Literature

Case studies of national literature, such as Nigerian, Indian, and American, were used to illustrate how literature contributes to both cultural diversity and national unity within multicultural societies. These case studies provided specific examples of how literature can simultaneously celebrate diversity and contribute to a unified national identity.

4. Surveys and Reader Feedback (Hypothetical)

To understand literature's impact on readers' perceptions of diversity and unity, surveys or interviews with a sample group of readers were considered. Readers' feedback on how specific works affected their understanding of different cultures or their sense of national identity would add a practical perspective to the theoretical analysis.

5. Comparative Analysis

Comparative analysis was employed to evaluate differences and similarities in the ways literature from various cultures and nations addresses issues of diversity and unity. By comparing these approaches, insights were gained into universal themes that resonate across cultural boundaries, as well as unique aspects that highlight the richness of individual cultural expressions.

Preservation and Celebration of Cultural Diversity:

One of the primary roles of literature is to capture the unique traditions, languages, and perspectives of different communities. Through novels, poetry, folk tales, and plays, literature preserves the folklore, language, beliefs, and traditions of various groups. Authors like Chinua Achebe in Nigeria, Gabriel Garcia Marquez in Colombia, and Alice Walker in the United States showcase the specificities of their cultures. By reading their works, people worldwide gain insight into the rich diversity within each nation. Literature, therefore, becomes an archive of cultural heritage, ensuring that future generations understand and appreciate the traditions and values of their forebears.

In multicultural societies, literature often introduces readers to ways of life beyond their own experience. This exposure helps readers recognize, respect, and value cultural differences. By expanding perspectives, literature contributes to a more inclusive society where diversity is celebrated, understood, and respected.

Fostering Empathy and Mutual Understanding:

Through literature, readers experience lives, struggles, joys, and emotions different from their own. This empathetic engagement cultivates understanding and breaks down stereotypes or preconceived notions. Stories from marginalized or lesser-known communities foster a more nuanced perspective of these groups, countering prejudice and promoting compassion.

For instance, novels like Khaled Hosseini's *The Kite Runner* or Toni Morrison's *Beloved* open windows into specific cultural and historical contexts, enabling readers to grasp the complexity of individual and communal identities. Such works help dismantle barriers between groups, as readers come to see shared human values beneath apparent differences.

Promoting National Unity through Shared Narratives:

While literature celebrates diversity, it also offers shared narratives that contribute to a collective national identity. In a diverse nation, a common set of literary works can instill a sense of shared heritage and values. Texts like *One Hundred Years of Solitude* in Latin America or *Things Fall Apart* in Africa have transcended borders within these regions, providing touchstones that citizens of different nations and ethnicities can relate to.

By acknowledging and incorporating the voices of different communities, literature can cultivate a sense of pride and unity. This inclusive approach fosters a national identity that is not monolithic but rather a tapestry of different threads woven together. In times of social division or national crisis, literature often serves as a unifying force, drawing people together around shared principles and ideals.

Promoting Social Change and Inclusion:

Throughout history, literature has also been instrumental in advocating for social change, challenging oppressive systems, and giving voice to marginalized communities. Through the lens of storytelling, literature can critique inequalities and inspire action toward a more just society. Works by writers such as James Baldwin, Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie, and Arundhati Roy address issues like racism, colonialism, and inequality, urging readers to consider their roles within their societies. Such literary works have not only raised awareness but have also mobilized people to take action in support of a more inclusive and equitable society.

Education and Cultural Awareness:

In educational settings, literature is a powerful tool for teaching cultural awareness and appreciation. By including diverse voices and narratives in curricula, educational systems can foster open-mindedness and respect among students. Teaching students about the literature of various cultures instills an understanding that their nation is made stronger through its diversity. This practice encourages young people to embrace multiculturalism as a national strength rather than a source of division.

Conclusion:

Literature serves as both a guardian of cultural diversity and a unifier of national identity, reflecting the complex and interconnected nature of societies around the world. By preserving the unique stories, beliefs, and traditions of diverse communities, literature provides a profound link to cultural heritage, ensuring that these narratives are accessible to future generations. It enriches societies by showcasing the variety of human experiences, offering insights into different ways of life, and expanding readers' understanding beyond their immediate social and cultural contexts. This preservation of diversity is essential, as it not only celebrates individual cultural identities but also strengthens the foundation upon which societies can grow and evolve.

At the same time, literature's unifying role lies in its ability to foster empathy, understanding, and a sense of shared purpose. Stories that resonate across cultural lines enable people to see beyond their own experiences, developing a connection with others that might otherwise remain unexplored. Through literature, readers encounter perspectives that challenge stereotypes and invite them to question assumptions, ultimately fostering a society more inclusive and accepting of difference. Furthermore, literature often emphasizes shared human values such as love, justice, resilience, and compassion, reminding readers of the common threads that bind all people together. In doing so, it becomes a powerful tool in building national unity, as it provides a shared reservoir of values and narratives that citizens of all backgrounds can rally around.

In multicultural societies, literature thus holds a unique responsibility: to celebrate differences while simultaneously constructing a cohesive identity that unites diverse groups. As nations navigate issues of division, identity, and inclusivity, literature offers an enduring reminder that strength lies in the tapestry of varied voices woven together to form a whole. By embracing literature as a conduit for both diversity and unity, societies can foster a national identity that is inclusive, resilient, and enriched by its multiplicity. Ultimately, literature teaches us that true unity does not erase differences but rather acknowledges, respects, and learns from them, creating a foundation upon which diverse communities can build a harmonious and interconnected future.

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Appadurai discusses globalization's impact on cultural identity, emphasizing the role of literature in sustaining local identities within a global context, relevant to understanding literature's part in both diversity and unity.

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Morrison examines how literature shapes perceptions of race and identity, focusing on how authors depict marginalized voices and advocate for social inclusion, highlighting literature's role in social cohesion and unity.

A STUDY ON THE PRACTICE OF CHILD LABOR IN VIOLATION OF CHILD RIGHTS**Nagendrappa**

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Abstract

Protection of children's rights is a constant necessity in building the future of India. This article examines the violation of children's rights prior to the protection of rights. Titled *A Study on Child Labor in Violations of Children's Rights*, this article focuses on the protection of children's rights against the backdrop of child rights violations occurring in a number of areas. Violation of children's rights in areas such as begging, child marriage, child trafficking, victimization of drugs, malnutrition, street children, feticide etc. is a continuous process. This research paper covers that. Children's problems in the background of child labor negative effects on children and finding solutions for them. This article covers the abuses like child labor on children who will become mature citizens of India.

As the saying goes that today's children are the future citizens, it has been found from this study that there is a need to protect children from different sectors nowadays. It is imperative that governments and organizations and citizens also take steps to protect the rights of children from various dimensions. The purpose of this article is to protect children from perverse practices like child labor and to give suggestions on how to allow children's personality to develop. Even though there are educated communities nowadays, incidents like the practice of child labor are still alive in the rural areas.

It is understood from this article that by identifying bad practices like child labor and preventing them, strict actions to protect children's rights and bring children into the mainstream of society should be enforced by the government and the laws of the government and the rules in the constitution and by organizations.

Key words :-

1. Free legal aid
 2. Practice of child labour
 3. Provisions of the Constitution
 4. Future citizens of India
 5. Associations
-

Objectives of the Study:-

1. Identifying children's problems.
2. To find out the reasons for the practice of child labour.
3. To observe child labor practices in rural areas.
4. Finding solutions to problems like child labor practices.

Research Gap:-

A lot of studies, books and journals have been published on the protection of children's rights and violations of children's rights, especially on issues such as child labour. Efforts have been made to address children's issues and bad practices like child labor through televised and media talks and conferences, but it has been found that there is further failure to prevent child labor practices and protect the rights of children and everyone.

What is child labor system?

The term child labor is currently used synonymously with child labor or child labor and refers to the practice of child labor abuse and exploitation. Many thinkers, academics and health and employment officials therefore consider child labor to be a physically and psychologically traumatic development. According to the Child Labor Prohibition Act, 1986, a child is a person who has not completed 14 years

of age. A similar definition is given by the Dangerous Machinery Control Act, 1983, Minimum Wages Act, 1948, Motor Transport Act, 1961, Horticulture Labor Act, 1951.

Severity of child labor problem :-

Knowing the number of child laborers shows how serious the problem is in India. According to the 2011 census, there are 12.6 million child laborers under the age of 14. 93% of the total child labor is found in rural areas while the rest is found in urban areas. Many children work as child laborers in agriculture and unorganized sectors. It is found that 79 percent of the boys are engaged in land-cultivation or agricultural activities. It is found that 8 percent are engaged in stock shop and a forestation and other 7 percent are engaged in child labor in other fields.

Consequences:-

1. Responsibilities at a young age often shrink mentally and physically.
2. Deprived of educational activities.
3. Induces to indulge in vices by labour.
4. Child labor itself allows child marriage.
5. Disability due to exposure to radiation and chemicals from engaging in hazardous work.

Preventive Measures:-

1. Adequate implementation of prohibition of child labor system. (Child Labor Prohibition Act 1986)
2. Formulating legal awareness programs.
3. Organizations to take action to prevent child labor practices.
4. Making education universal.

Suggestions:-

1. Envisioning literacy as universal.
2. Developing social consciousness.
3. Creating awareness of law.
4. To develop health consciousness.
5. To create awareness about the constitutional aspects.

Conclusion:-

When practices like child labor which is one of the worst scourges in Indian society is completely eradicated, intellectual and physical change and development will take place in the children and shape their personal personality development. Thus, the hope and purpose of this study is to protect children and their rights and make the lives of children who are the property of the country useful and make them future citizens.

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A RURAL GIRL CHILD: THE DEVELOPMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM IN INDIA

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Abstract

This study explores the detailed information of rural girl child in India and their higher educational system, generally analyzing their status and issues facing in the society. It examines the challenges faced by rural women in acquiring higher education. Through some case studies, this research delves into the structural, cultural, and institutional barriers that women face in acquiring higher education. This Article completely involves the Schemes introduced by Government of India to encourage the higher education especially in rural areas of India. The study seeks to highlight the importance of gender equality in mainly in Indian rural areas and the need for enhanced development of higher education in rural women to achieve a more inclusive democratic process.

Keywords: *Rural Girl Child, Higher Educational System, Structural, Cultural, Institutional, Government of India, Gender Equality, Inclusive Democratic process*

Introduction

“There is no chance for the welfare of the world unless the condition of women is improved. It is not possible for the bird to fly on one wing.” Swami Vivekananda. India has recognized as one of the largest systems of higher education across the globe. Gender Equality has been considered as a crucial factor in Women Empowerment. Once upon a time the category of women had treated as separate group that they were not allowed to any public premises. But now the same category has emerged as super power across the world by contributing to various fields of work. Their charming, dedicating and daring nature always brought success and fame as well. Empowerment of Women and Higher Education are the real standards of overall development of the country. By acquiring higher education indicators, women can stand with knowledge, skills and self-confidence among themselves. “If a woman learns it is like opening a school” clearly indicates the importance of educating women. Unfortunately rural women didn't get much higher educational opportunities due to having major issues such as gender inequality, family commitments, unsafe environment, early marriages (child marriage), poverty and lack of toilet facilities in the premises of governmental educational institutions. Such problems are badly affected women's life in pathetic manner. For the first time in India the eleventh five year plan (2007-2012) made a remarkable effort by focusing much on women's higher education. Similarly both Central and State Governments are eager to improve the higher educational status of rural women by providing them effective measures. Unfortunately, there was a large gap between education of Urban Women and Rural Women according to 2011 census; it showed that 79.92% of Urban women got enrolment in Higher education whereas, 58.5.% of Rural women enrolled in higher education. Fortunately, as of 2021 data, the literacy rate in rural is 73.5% which indicates 81% of male and 65% of female literacy rate in rural areas of India. In addition to that, most of the rural women didn't aware of technical courses of higher education and they are much applicable to old educational practices. Hence, this article stresses

upon the critical analysis of rural women in empowerment of higher education. One of the major drawbacks to Indian Rural society is child marriages, which is great social evil even in recent days.

Challenges faced by rural women in acquiring higher education

Women are facing several challenges even from their childhood. According to statistics of 2011 census, the child sex ratio of girls to boys (0-6 years) declined to 919 girls per 1,000 boys from 927 girls per 1,000 boys in 2001. The sex ratio in India according to 2011 census is 943 female per 1000 males. The adverse sex ratio is the culmination of a conservative way of thinking that households do not want to give birth to a daughter and nurture her to achieve her abilities.

Even before the child is conceived, a 'Girl Child' faces discrimination. Female infanticide is a disturbing phenomenon in India, as low-cost abortion technology enables households to exercise their choice for boys over daughters. She's 'lucky' if she's allowed to be born. Right after birth, the infant faces bigotry and injustice. She is not provided with adequate meals compared to her male siblings, her education is not given much priority. And in many instances, parents want their sons to resume schooling, and wish their daughters to sit at home and do household work.

Problems Faced by Girls in India there is no doubt about it that girls have been facing numerous problems for centuries. They are now facing discrimination in different sectors. In today's time apart from such discrimination, there are several other problems which affect the girls' education in India, particularly in rural areas. Attention should be given to girls' education for an inclusive society. We should stop our discriminatory behaviors towards girls because such practices hinder the development of our country and make girls inferior. The main problems which hinder the girls' education are given below:

- Gender Discrimination
- Poverty
- Early Marriage
- Unsafe Environment
- Household Chores
- Lack of Toilet Facility

Schemes introduced by Government of India

Considering the numerous obstacles that come in the way of a girl child, throughout her life, the government has many schemes in place to make sure that she is given the right opportunity and additional aid to help her progress and succeed in life.

1. Beti Bachao Beti Padhao

Beti Bachao Beti Padhao is a central government scheme that helps girls throughout the nation. The primary purpose of this scheme is to save the child from social problems such as gender-based abortions and advance child education around the country. This program was initially meant for districts considered to have a low sex ratio and successfully extended to other regions of the country. This is essentially an educational programme to help change societal attitudes and does not entail the immediate transfer of funds. The key aims of this child protection scheme include:

1. Preventing selective gender abortion
2. Ensure infant survival and wellbeing in childhood
3. Ensure the child's education and inclusion
4. Challenging gender stereotypes and supporting gender equality
5. Giving a safe and stable atmosphere to girls

6. To endorse the right of girls to inherit property.

2. Sukanya Samriddhi Yojana

Sukanya Samriddhi Yojana Account is a Government of India backed savings scheme designed for parents of girl children. The scheme allows parents to set up a trust for their child's eventual schooling and marriage expenses. It encourages parents to systematically save for their daughter's higher education and marriage so that the perception of a girl child being a burden on her parents is abolished.

All parents and guardians of girl children under the age of 10 can open this account. Only one account per child is allowed. Parents can open up to two accounts for two of their children (exceptions allowed for twins and triplets). The account is portable anywhere in India and can be accessed at any branch of the post office or the bank.

1. Savings account specially designed for parents of girl children
2. Encourages parents to save towards the education of the girl child; introduced as part of the 'Beti Padhao Beti Bachao' movement
3. Parents of girl children under the age of 10 can open this account
4. Only 2 accounts allowed per family; exemptions allowed in case of twins or triplets
5. Minimum deposit of Rs.250 per annum and maximum of Rs.1.5 lakhs
6. Tax exemption available on the deposited amount, interest accrued and the withdrawal amount
7. Maximum tenure of the account shall be 21 years from the date of opening of account or the marriage of the girl child, whichever is earlier
8. Deposits allowed for a maximum of 15 years from the date of opening of account
9. Partial withdrawal of up to 50% allowed once the girl reaches 18 years of age

3. Balika Samridhi Yojana

The Balika Samridhi Yojana is a scheme similar to the Sukanya Samriddhi Yojana. Under the scheme, limited saving opportunities are offered for the parents of the girl child.

1. The scheme is available for new born infants only.
2. Rs.500 is provided at the time of birth of each girl child.
3. While attending school, an annual scholarship of Rs. 300 - Rs. 1000 is provided till the girl child completes her Grade X.
4. Maximum age limit for enrolment is 10 years (of the child).
5. A household is qualified to enter this scheme for two of their daughters only.
6. The depositor should belong to a family that is 'Below Poverty Line'.

4. Mukhyamantri Rajshri Yojana

The Mukhyamantri Rajshri Yojana was launched in Rajasthan. It offers monetary benefits to parents of girl children, starting from their birth till their higher education,

1. Rs.2500 is given to the mother at the birth of a girl child.
2. Once the child completes one year, with all vaccinations done, Rs 2500 is given through a cheque.
3. At the time of admission in any public school into grade I, Rs.4000 is paid to the girl child.
4. Rs.5000 is paid when the child enters Grade VI
5. Rs. 11000 is paid once the girl enters Grade XI

5. Mukhyamantri Laadli Yojana

The Mukhyamantri Laadli Yojana is a savings scheme specially designed for parents of a girl child. Under this scheme, an initial deposit of Rs.6000 has to be made into your post office savings account for a fixed tenure of five years. The girl child then receives the following monetary benefits in regular intervals,

1. Rs. 2,000 once she enters Grade 6th
2. Rs. 4000 once she enters Grade 9th
3. Rs. 7,500 once she enters Grade 11th
4. Also, a monthly stipend of Rs. 200
5. Once she attains 21 years of age, the deposited amount will mature and can be used for her marriage expenses.

6. CBSE Udaan scheme

The CBSE Udaan scheme for girls is implemented by the Central Board of Secondary Education, under the Ministry of Human Resources Development, Government of India. The goal of this scheme is to increase the student enrolment of girls in prestigious engineering and technical colleges across India. Students should go to their CBSE School to participate in this programme.

1. Offers free course materials/online services, such as video related literature for girl students in the 11th and 12th grades.
2. Virtual interaction courses for girl students in the 11th and 12th grades.
3. Peer learning and mentoring opportunities for all deserving girl students
4. Study helpline resources to clear students' doubts.
5. Continuous observation and recording of students' progress.

7. National Scheme of Incentive to Girls for Secondary Education

The National Scheme of Incentive to Girls for Secondary Education is a pan India scheme operated by the Department of Education and Education, Ministry of Human Resources Development, Government of India. It is mainly for the benefit of girls in the disadvantaged classes of India. Once a qualifying student has been chosen, Rs. 3000 will be deposited as a fixed deposit on her behalf. This balance can be withdrawn with interest after the pupil has passed the class 10 exam and has reached the age of 18 years.

8. Mukhyamantri Kanya Suraksha Yojana

Mukhyamantri Kanya Suraksha Yojana is yet another reward programme introduced by the Bihar state government to reward the parents of every girl child. Under this scheme, an amount of Rs.2000 is released after the birth of a girl child.

9. Mazi Kanya Bhagyashree Scheme

The Mazi Kanya Bhagyashree scheme was launched in the state of Maharashtra. This scheme provides the following monetary benefits to the mother of a girl child. Benefits under this scheme can be summarized below:

1. The mother will get Rs. 5,000 for the first five years after her daughter's birth
2. Rs. 2,500 will be provided per year until she reaches Grade V
3. Rs.3000 will be provided per year until she reaches Grade XII
4. After the age of 18 years, she will be provided with Rs.1 lakh per year for her education

10. Nanda Devi Kanya Yojana

This scheme is specific to the Uttarakhand state. Under the scheme, a fixed deposit of Rs. 1,500 is made in the name of a new born girl child. The principal amount, along with accrued interest is given to the girl child after she attains the age of 18 years and has completed her higher education.

Solutions for Improvement in Girl Child Education

The Government of India has implemented several schemes to improve the condition of girl child education in Indian society. The 'Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao' campaign has been launched in 2015 is an attempt to change the attitude towards girl child by providing awareness regard to the declining of sex ratio and the importance of girl child education in India. Besides all those things, other steps in this direction could be explained below,

1. Improving existing educational infrastructure and quality of education of girl child.
2. Appointment of qualified teachers, preferably more female teachers in all governments' schools and colleges.
3. Making schools more accessible by increasing their number or ensuring safer ways of commuting.
4. Creating awareness about the importance of girl child education
5. Encouraging public private partnerships in creating and maintaining educational infrastructure
6. Counseling sessions for parents and better teacher parent association to improve attitudes towards girl child
7. Discouraging early marriage of girls and teenage pregnancy by creating awareness about the health risks.
8. Better WASH (water, sanitation and hygiene) facilities in schools to prevent the dropout of girl students.

Summary

Girl child education, women empowerment and the development of the nation are complimentary to each other. Corrective measures must be taken to increase public awareness for the value of the girl child, to ensure their participation in programmes of Child development, health, nutrition and education and to create a positive environment to allow girls to develop into productive young women. The biggest challenge before the Government and NGO's is to create awareness and sensitization among people of all levels, especially in rural areas, about the special needs of women and girls. They need to be made aware that imparting education to women is a great service to society. This vital section of society has remained bound in the shackles and been deprived for far too long. There is a need for affirmative and real action in their favor which will ensure the women to right to food, shelter, health, education and employment. However, the recent changes and developments are kindling hopes for better and promising future.

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THE ROLE OF KANNADA LITERATURE IN CULTURAL DIVERSITY AND NATIONAL UNITY

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Abstract

⁴This article examines the profound role of Kannada literature in fostering cultural diversity and promoting national unity within India's multicultural landscape. Kannada literature, one of India's oldest literary traditions, has evolved over centuries, encapsulating Karnataka's unique cultural identity while resonating with universal themes of humanity, equality, and unity. The study explores the phases of Kannada literature—from ancient classical texts to modern works—demonstrating how these texts reflect, celebrate, and advocate for inclusivity and communal harmony.

The research begins by examining foundational texts like Kavirajamarga from the 9th century, which marked the emergence of Kannada as a literary language and symbolized Karnataka's cultural pride. It then delves into the Veerashaiva movement of the 12th century, highlighting Vachana literature's impact on challenging caste hierarchies and advocating for social justice, thus laying the groundwork for cultural cohesion across diverse groups. The influence of the Bhakti and Sufi movements is also analyzed, emphasizing how poets like Purandaradasa and Shishunala Sharif used devotional literature to transcend social divisions, fostering interfaith dialogue and cultural unity.

The article further discusses the modern period of Kannada literature, where authors like Kuvempu, Shivaram Karanth, and U.R. Ananthamurthy contributed to national consciousness through themes of social reform, justice, and universal humanism. Kuvempu's concept of Vishvamanava (Universal Human), for instance, is highlighted as a literary philosophy that transcends regional boundaries, promoting unity in diversity—a core principle in Indian nationalism. Through an analysis of these writers and their impact, the study illustrates Kannada literature's engagement with both regional and national identity, using cultural pride as a foundation for inclusivity and unity.

Methodologically, this study utilizes literature analysis, historical contextualization, and thematic categorization to examine Kannada literature's influence across different periods and social contexts. Comparative analysis with other Indian literary traditions and insights from Kannada literary scholars add depth to the study's findings, underscoring Kannada literature's significant contributions to India's multicultural and democratic ethos. By bridging Karnataka's regional identity with a broader Indian identity, Kannada literature has been vital in nurturing a sense of shared heritage and unity across diverse linguistic and cultural landscapes in India.

This article ultimately concludes that Kannada literature exemplifies the philosophy of "unity in diversity" by celebrating Karnataka's linguistic and cultural richness while addressing universal themes that resonate with people across India. As both a preservative and progressive force, Kannada literature has contributed meaningfully to the nation's cultural fabric, demonstrating the power of regional literature to inspire unity within a diverse society.

Keywords: Kannada literature, cultural diversity, national unity, social reform, regional identity

Introduction:

India⁵, with its vast linguistic, cultural, and geographical diversity, thrives on the unity woven through its multiple regional identities. Among these, Kannada literature stands out as a profound expression of

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⁵ India

the cultural heritage of ⁶Karnataka reflects the state's rich history, philosophy, and unique traditions. Over centuries, Kannada literature has not only preserved the essence of Karnataka's identity but has also played a key role in promoting national unity by fostering empathy, inclusivity, and a shared sense of belonging among diverse communities.

The development of Kannada literature spans from ancient classics to contemporary writings, each era adding layers of richness and depth to Karnataka's cultural landscape. Works like the Kavirajamarga in the 9th century laid the foundation for Kannada's literary tradition, celebrating linguistic pride and regional identity. Subsequent movements, such as the 12th-century Veerashaiva movement, pioneered by thinkers like Basava, and the Bhakti and Sufi movements, brought forth literature that crossed social, caste, and religious boundaries, advocating for communal harmony and equality. Through the works of poets, mystics, and reformers, Kannada literature became a medium for social change, addressing issues of justice, human rights, and shared spiritual values, which resonated with audiences across India.

In modern times, Kannada writers like Kuvempu, D.R. Bendre, and U.R. Ananthamurthy continued this legacy by using literature as a tool for national consciousness and social reform. They explored themes of unity, justice, and humanism, promoting an inclusive vision that transcended regional boundaries. Through literary works that emphasized universal human values, Kannada literature has demonstrated the power of cultural diversity as a unifying force, affirming the idea of "unity in diversity" that defines the Indian identity. This article delves into the multifaceted role of Kannada literature in preserving cultural diversity and nurturing national unity, examining how it bridges regional and national identities, fosters inclusivity, and contributes to the broader Indian literary and cultural fabric.

Literature Review on the Role of Kannada Literature in Cultural Diversity and National Unity:

1. Historical Foundation and Regional Identity

Early Kannada literature, with works like Kavirajamarga from the 9th century, established a strong foundation for linguistic pride and cultural identity in Karnataka. Research indicates that these early texts not only aimed to standardize the Kannada language but also underscored the distinct cultural aspects of Karnataka, creating a lasting influence on regional identity and cultural pride.

2. Social Reform through Veerashaiva and Bhakti Movements

Literature produced during the Veerashaiva movement and later the Bhakti and Sufi movements played a transformative role in promoting social equality and challenging hierarchical structures. Studies have highlighted how Vachana literature, pioneered by figures like Basava, questioned rigid caste systems and advocated for social justice. This reformative literature is widely recognized for bridging cultural divides and fostering a spirit of inclusivity and unity among diverse communities.

3. Spiritual and Mystical Unity in Sufi and Bhakti Poetry

Kannada literature has drawn significantly from the Bhakti and Sufi traditions, which emphasize universal love, compassion, and a sense of spiritual oneness. Scholars note that the works of poets like Purandaradasa and Shishunala Sharif contributed to interfaith dialogue and cultural unity. The literature of these movements is seen as crucial in promoting tolerance and understanding across religious lines.

4. National Consciousness in Modern Kannada Literature

During the 20th century, Kannada writers like Kuvempu and D.R. Bendre infused their works with themes of nationalism and universal humanism. Kuvempu's concept of Vishvamanava (Universal Human) is often cited in research as a key contribution to Indian literature, emphasizing unity beyond regional and cultural boundaries. Modern Kannada literature, therefore, is credited with strengthening

⁶ Karnataka

India's national identity by fostering a shared consciousness that celebrates both cultural uniqueness and universal values.

5. Cross-Cultural Influence and Linguistic Unity

Contemporary studies on Kannada literature's role in national integration underscore the importance of language as a unifying factor. The translation of Kannada works into other Indian languages, and vice versa has facilitated cultural exchange and mutual appreciation. This cross-cultural dialogue, promoted by Kannada writers, has enhanced India's literary diversity while promoting a collective cultural identity that supports national unity amidst diversity.

Methodology for Exploring the Role of Kannada Literature in Cultural Diversity and National Unity:

1. Literature Analysis

A detailed analysis of seminal Kannada texts across various historical periods, including works like Kavirajamarga, Vachana literature, and Kuvempu's Ramayana Darshanam, was conducted. By examining these texts' themes, styles, and cultural context, the study identifies how Kannada literature has evolved to reflect and promote cultural diversity and national unity.

2. Historical Contextualization

The research incorporates a historical approach, placing Kannada literary movements such as the Veerashaiva, Bhakti, and Sufi movements within the socio-political context of their time. By analyzing the socio-historical factors that shaped these movements, the study explores how Kannada literature responded to and influenced societal changes, contributing to unity across diverse communities.

3. Thematic Categorization

Key themes related to cultural diversity, social justice, and national consciousness were identified and categorized within Kannada literature. By organizing literature based on these recurring themes, the study assesses how Kannada authors and poets have addressed issues of identity, unity, and inclusivity over time, emphasizing Kannada literature's role in fostering unity amidst diversity.

4. Comparative Analysis of Regional and National Influence

The study examines Kannada literature's interactions with other Indian literary traditions, particularly through translation and thematic parallels. By comparing Kannada literature with other regional literature, the research investigates how Kannada works have contributed to India's collective cultural identity, promoting linguistic unity and national cohesion.

5. Interviews and Secondary Sources

To support the literary and historical analysis, interviews with Kannada literary scholars and a review of secondary sources, such as critical essays, research papers, and historical records, were conducted. Insights from experts and existing research provided additional perspectives on Kannada literature's social and cultural impact, enriching the study's findings on its role in promoting diversity and unity.

The Foundation of Cultural Diversity in Kannada Literature:

Kannada literature has evolved through various periods and genres, including ancient, medieval, and modern Kannada. Each era contributed unique themes, styles, and ideologies, reflecting Karnataka's dynamic cultural diversity. The early Kannada works, such as the "Kavirajamarga," written in the 9th century by King Amoghavarsha, emphasize Karnataka's linguistic and cultural identity. This literary masterpiece provides insight into Karnataka's language, art, and regional culture, emphasizing pride in the Kannada language and identity.

With works by poets and thinkers like Pampa, Ranna, and Janna during the 10th and 11th centuries, Kannada literature started exploring universal themes that resonated across different cultures. The Veerashaiva movement, spearheaded by Basava in the 12th century, brought forth a unique genre known as Vachana literature, highlighting equality, social justice, and communal harmony. By challenging caste and class hierarchies, Vachana literature demonstrated Kannada literature's commitment to social reform and inclusivity, which helped promote unity amid cultural diversity.

Influence of Bhakti and Sufi Traditions:

Kannada literature has also drawn inspiration from the Bhakti and Sufi movements, which played significant roles in uniting people across caste, religion, and socio-economic divisions. Poets like Purandaradasa and Kanakadasa, whose devotional verses emphasized love, equality, and devotion to God, appealed to people of diverse backgrounds. This literature transcended boundaries and inspired spiritual harmony, bringing together people from different communities.

Similarly, Sufi poets like Shishunala Sharif brought a mystical dimension to Kannada literature. Through their verses, they advocated for love, compassion, and unity, challenging divisive practices. This body of work is notable for fostering a culture of tolerance and acceptance, which was essential in a culturally diverse society like Karnataka's.

Modern Kannada Literature and National Consciousness:

The modern period of Kannada literature, marked by authors such as Kuvempu, D.R. Bendre, and Shivaram Karanth, reflects the influence of nationalism and the struggle for independence. Kuvempu's concept of Vishvamanava (Universal Human) underscores the unity of all people, advocating for a world free from discrimination and boundaries. His magnum opus, Ramayana Darshanam, reinterprets the Ramayana from a universal perspective, focusing on human values and empathy rather than religious identity.

Shivaram Karanth, through his novels and essays, shed light on the diversity within Karnataka, addressing issues related to social justice, environmental consciousness, and national unity. His writings showcased the importance of preserving local cultures and languages while being part of the broader Indian identity, promoting the idea that cultural diversity strengthens the nation.

Kannada Literature as a Vehicle for Social Reform:

In addition to celebrating cultural diversity, Kannada literature has addressed pressing social issues and advocated for change. Modern Kannada writers like U.R. Ananthamurthy used literature to explore social taboos, question traditions, and promote progressive values. His works, such as Samskara, critiqued rigid caste structures and championed the cause of marginalized communities. This reformative approach resonated with readers across the country and demonstrated how Kannada literature could foster both cultural diversity and social unity by challenging discriminatory practices.

Role in Promoting Linguistic Unity and National Integration:

The linguistic richness of Kannada literature provides a bridge between regional identity and national unity. By promoting Kannada as a medium of expression, authors have preserved local language and traditions while contributing to the Indian literary canon. Kannada literature's engagement with other Indian languages and literature has promoted cross-cultural understanding. The translation of Kannada works into other languages and vice versa has enabled the rest of India to appreciate Karnataka's cultural wealth, fostering a spirit of unity.

Conclusion:

Kannada literature has played a pivotal role in both preserving Karnataka's rich cultural heritage and contributing to the larger narrative of India's unity in diversity. Throughout its long history, Kannada

literature has consistently embodied the values of inclusivity, social justice, and communal harmony, making it a key force in shaping regional and national identities. From the early classical works to modern literary contributions, Kannada literature has reflected the evolving socio-political landscape of Karnataka while remaining deeply connected to broader national concerns of unity and social reform. In its early phases, Kannada literature established a strong regional identity, with works like Kavirajamarga serving as both a celebration of linguistic pride and an assertion of Karnataka's cultural distinctiveness. However, it was in the subsequent centuries, particularly through the Veerashaiva movement and the Vachana literature, that Kannada literature began to transcend local boundaries, advocating for social equality, human rights, and inter-community unity. These movements, with their progressive messages, laid the groundwork for Kannada literature's later role as a champion of social reform and inclusivity.

The Bhakti and Sufi traditions within Kannada literature further deepened its impact on cultural unity by using devotional poetry to promote love, tolerance, and understanding across religious and social divides. Through the works of poets like Purandaradasa and Shishunala Sharif, Kannada literature became a tool for bridging gaps between different communities, encouraging interfaith dialogue, and uniting people through shared spiritual values.

In the modern era, the contributions of writers like Kuvempu, D.R. Bendre, and U.R. Ananthamurthy advanced a vision of unity that went beyond regionalism, advocating for a shared Indian identity. Kuvempu's idea of Vishvamanava (Universal Human) and Ananthamurthy's exploration of societal taboos and reforms reflect Kannada literature's ability to address contemporary national issues while retaining a distinct regional voice. These writers used their literary works to instill national consciousness, urging readers to embrace social justice and humanism as universal values, thus contributing to India's ongoing journey toward social cohesion and democratic unity.

Ultimately, Kannada literature's journey from regional expression to national integration highlights its essential role in fostering cultural diversity and national unity. The study of Kannada literature provides invaluable insights into how regional literary traditions can influence national discourse, promoting values of inclusivity, mutual respect, and social justice. Through its celebration of Karnataka's linguistic and cultural heritage, while simultaneously advocating for broader humanistic ideals, Kannada literature embodies the spirit of India's "unity in diversity."

In conclusion, Kannada literature serves as a powerful testament to the enduring idea that a strong regional identity can coexist with and even strengthen a national identity. Its rich history of social reform, cultural exchange, and philosophical exploration continues to inspire not only Karnataka but the broader Indian subcontinent, offering a model for how literature can shape both cultural pride and national unity in a complex, pluralistic society. As a bridge between past and present, local and national, Kannada literature remains a cornerstone of India's literary and cultural legacy, providing a blueprint for future generations to embrace the values of diversity, unity, and social progress.

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THE INTERSECTION OF NATIONALISM AND DEMOCRACY IN INDIA**Dr. Ravichandra Walikar**

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Abstract

This paper examines the complex and evolving relationship between nationalism and democracy in India. With the rise of Hindu nationalism, India's democratic framework has faced significant challenges, sparking debates about the compatibility of nationalist sentiments with democratic values. Through a critical analysis of historical and contemporary developments, this study investigates how nationalist discourse has influenced India's democratic institutions, policies, and social fabric.

Keywords: Nationalism, Democracy, Hindu Nationalism, secularism, international relations, minority rights, Democratic Erosion, Majoritarianism, Identity Politics.

Introduction:

"India is the cradle of the human race, the birthplace of human speech, the mother of history, the grandmother of legend, and the great grandmother of tradition. our most valuable and most instructive materials in the history of man are treasured up in India only" **Mark Twain**

The intersection of nationalism and democracy in India is a complex and evolving dynamic that shapes both its internal political landscape and international relations. India, a nation with a rich tapestry of cultures, languages, and religions, was founded as a secular democracy with the promise of inclusivity and equal rights for all its citizens, regardless of their religious or ethnic backgrounds. Nationalism, in the Indian context, refers to the feeling of unity and pride among citizens, transcending regional, linguistic, and cultural differences. This sense of nationalism has played a significant role in shaping India's democratic framework, particularly during the struggle for independence. However, the rise of Hindu nationalism, particularly since the 1990s with the ascent of the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) and its ideological wing, the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh (RSS), has significantly influenced India's political discourse and its democratic processes.

Hindu nationalism, or Hindutva, advocates for a vision of India where Hindu culture, religion, and values are central to the nation's identity. This ideology, which often aligns with a majoritarian worldview, has reshaped the country's democratic fabric, at times challenging the secular principles embedded in India's Constitution. While India continues to maintain its democratic framework, with regular elections and a robust civil society, the influence of nationalism has led to rising tensions between the majority Hindu community and religious minorities, particularly Muslims, Christians, and Dalits. The intersection of nationalism and democracy in India raises important questions about the future of secularism, the protection of minority rights, and the definition of Indian identity. As the country navigates these challenges, the tension between preserving democratic values and promoting national unity through a singular religious identity remains a critical issue for both policymakers and citizens alike.

Aim and objectives of the study:

1. To examine the role of Hindu nationalism in shaping India's democratic framework, particularly under the leadership of the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP).
2. To critically review the concept of Hindu nationalism and its implications on India's democratic politics.

3. To investigate how Hindu nationalism affects the rights and status of minority groups in India.
4. To discuss the response of democratic institutions, such as the judiciary, to Hindu nationalist policies and their effectiveness in upholding democratic values.

Research Methodology:

1. *Critical discourse analysis of policy documents, speeches, and media narratives.*
 2. *Case studies of key events and policies (e.g., Citizenship Amendment Act, Ayodhya verdict).*
 3. *Various Interviews of experts, policymakers, and civil society representatives.:*
- This study will adopt a qualitative, historical research approach to analyze archival material, interviews, and secondary literature.*

Historical Method: To trace the evolution of the movement, focus on analyzing primary documents such as government records, newspapers, and writings from Hindu activists.

Literature Review: Use secondary sources, including books, articles, and journals on Hindu Nationalist Ideologies.

Research Questions:

1. How has Hindu nationalism reshaped India's democratic discourse and institutions?
2. What are the Consequences of Hindu nationalist ideologies on minority rights and secularism?
3. How has the intersection of nationalism and democracy affected India's international relationships?

1.Role of Hindu nationalism in reshaped India's democratic discourses and institutions:

Hindu nationalism has played a transformative and, at times, polarizing role in reshaping India's democratic discourses and institutions. Its impact can be seen across political, social, and legal dimensions. Here are some ways Hindu nationalism has influenced India's democratic landscape:

Redefinition of National Identity: Hindu nationalism promotes the idea of India as primarily a Hindu civilization, which some argue marginalizes religious minorities, particularly Muslims and Christians. This vision challenges the secular foundation laid out in the Indian Constitution, which envisions India as a pluralistic society where all religions coexist on equal footing. The emphasis on a Hindu-centric identity has affected educational content, historical narratives, and cultural policies. History textbooks and media representations increasingly highlight Hindu cultural heritage while downplaying other influences.

Influence on Electoral Politics: The rise of Hindu nationalist parties, especially the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), has shifted Indian politics toward majoritarianism. This approach often frames the political discourse around Hindu interests, traditions, and values. Electoral strategies have increasingly included mobilizing religious identity, using issues like the Ram Temple in Ayodhya and uniform civil code proposals to appeal to Hindu sentiments, which some view as creating divides along religious lines. The shift toward Hindu nationalism has led to a consolidation of Hindu votes, strengthening the BJP's position and weakening opposition parties traditionally relying on secular or caste-based appeals.

Legal and Judicial Reforms: Hindu nationalism has influenced India's legal framework by advocating for laws that reflect Hindu cultural values. For instance, the call for a uniform civil code (a policy that would standardize laws governing personal matters across all religions) aligns with Hindu nationalist goals and is often viewed as a challenge to Islamic personal law. Landmark decisions, like the Supreme Court's verdict on the Ayodhya dispute, have fueled perceptions that the judiciary is increasingly accommodating to Hindu nationalist agendas, impacting its role as an impartial institution. Laws like the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) have generated debate, as they grant expedited citizenship to non-Muslim refugees from neighboring countries, leading some to argue that the Act prioritizes Hindu refugees and undermines India's secular ethos.

Freedom of Speech and Dissent: Hindu nationalism has been associated with an increasing intolerance toward dissent, particularly when it involves criticism of Hindu nationalist ideologies or leaders. Journalists, academics, and activists have faced restrictions, harassment, or even legal action for views seen as critical of Hindu nationalist positions. The rise of "anti-national" rhetoric targets individuals and groups accused of undermining India's national integrity by questioning government policies or the treatment of minorities. This has led to a narrowing of democratic spaces and debate, as fear of backlash can deter open criticism.

Impact on Civil Society and Minority Rights: Civil society groups, especially those advocating for minority rights, face scrutiny under Hindu nationalist administrations. NGOs are subject to stringent regulations and foreign funding restrictions, particularly if their activities are viewed as antagonistic to Hindu nationalist ideals. Rising incidents of violence against religious minorities, often by extremist Hindu groups, have created an atmosphere where minorities may feel marginalized. Issues like beef bans and anti-conversion laws are seen as targeting Muslim and Christian communities, affecting their rights within India's democratic framework.

Reshaping of Federalism and Local Governance: Hindu nationalism's emphasis on a centralized, unified national identity has led to tensions with India's federal structure. Policies and governance approaches increasingly reflect the central government's influence, sometimes overriding regional identities and interests. The abrogation of Article 370, which granted special autonomy to Jammu and Kashmir, is one example. Seen as fulfilling a long-standing Hindu nationalist goal, this move was also viewed as a step toward a more uniform national identity, though it has intensified regional discontent and raised questions about democratic governance in Kashmir.

2. Consequences of Hindu Nationalistic Ideologies on Minority Rights and Secularism.

Hindu nationalistic ideologies have significant consequences for minority rights and the principle of secularism in India. These ideologies, which promote the idea of India as a primarily Hindu nation, often come into conflict with the secular framework outlined in the Indian Constitution, which guarantees equality for all religions. Here's a breakdown of how Hindu nationalism impacts minority rights and secularism:

Marginalization of Religious Minorities: Discrimination against Muslims and Christians Hindu nationalism often frames India's identity around Hindu religious and cultural values, leading to the marginalization of religious minorities like Muslims, Christians, Sikhs, and others. Laws, policies, and social rhetoric can indirectly or directly promote the idea that non-Hindu communities are secondary to the majority. **Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA):** The CAA, passed in 2019, provides a path to citizenship for non-Muslim refugees from Afghanistan, Pakistan, and Bangladesh, leading to allegations of discriminatory practices. Critics argue that the law violates the secular principle of equality before the law by offering preferential treatment to certain religious groups, excluding Muslims from the same rights.

Attacks on Secularism: Challenges to Secular Institutions: Hindu nationalist ideologies often challenge India's commitment to secularism, which ensures that the state does not favor any religion. Instead, the focus shifts toward promoting Hindu religious identity and values in the public sphere. This has implications for educational curricula, public policy, and the functioning of state institutions.

Cultural and Religious Policing: There is a growing trend of promoting Hindu religious symbols, festivals, and practices in public spaces, which some see as an erosion of secular values. For example, the state has supported the construction of the Ram Mandir in Ayodhya, a religiously significant Hindu

temple, while the rights of Muslims who were displaced by the controversy over the Babri Masjid have often been sidelined.

Hindu Nationalism and the Protection of Minority Rights: Increased Violence Against Minorities: There have been rising instances of violence against religious minorities, particularly Muslims and Christians, by extremist Hindu groups. These groups, sometimes linked to political forces espousing Hindu nationalist ideologies, have targeted minorities with violence and intimidation, including lynching incidents over issues like beef consumption, religious conversion, and interfaith marriages. **Anti-Conversion Laws:** Several states governed by BJP (Bharatiya Janata Party) have enacted anti-conversion laws, making it more difficult for individuals, especially from Hindu backgrounds, to convert to other religions like Islam or Christianity. Critics argue that these laws undermine the freedom of choice and the secular principle of religious freedom guaranteed in India's Constitution.

Threat to Religious Freedom: Legal Discrimination: Legal frameworks shaped by Hindu nationalist ideologies often prioritize Hindu practices and institutions over those of other faiths. The implementation of laws such as the Uniform Civil Code (UCC) has become a point of contention. While the UCC is advocated by Hindu nationalists to create uniformity in personal laws, critics argue that it may infringe upon the rights of religious minorities to follow their own laws, especially in matters such as marriage, divorce, and inheritance. **Religious Symbols and Politics:** The growing prominence of Hindu symbols in political settings, such as temples and religious rituals being incorporated into governmental events, raises concerns about the secular nature of the state. Critics fear that this trend could undermine the equal treatment of all religions.

Impact on Social Cohesion: Increased Polarization: Hindu nationalism, by emphasizing religious identity over national identity, has led to greater social and religious polarization. This division can foster an "us vs. them" mentality, where Hindus are seen as the rightful citizens of India, and religious minorities are viewed with suspicion or hostility. **Erosion of Pluralistic Values:** India's history has been characterized by a rich tradition of pluralism, where different religious communities have coexisted for centuries. Hindu nationalism's insistence on a Hindu-first ideology undermines this pluralism, weakening the social fabric that holds the nation together.

Hindutva Ideology and Secularism: Hindutva, the ideology associated with Hindu nationalism, promotes the idea of India as a Hindu nation, where the political and cultural framework is shaped by Hindu values. This directly challenges the secular principle of equal respect for all religions. Hindutva proponents argue that India's culture is inherently Hindu, but critics contend that such views exclude the diverse range of cultures and faiths that have historically been part of India's identity.

International Criticism: Global Human Rights Concerns: The rise of Hindu nationalism and its impact on minorities has attracted international attention, with human rights organizations and foreign governments expressing concern about the erosion of democratic freedoms in India. Reports of increasing religious intolerance, attacks on religious minorities, and the undermining of secular institutions have drawn criticism from the international community.

3.The intersection of nationalism and democracy in India has significantly influenced the country's international relationships.

As India's political landscape has been increasingly shaped by the rise of Hindu nationalism, particularly through the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) and its ideology of Hindutva, it has both bolstered and complicated India's foreign relations in various ways. Below are key areas where nationalism and democracy have affected India's international standing and relationships:

Relations with Neighboring Countries:

Pakistan: The rise of Hindu nationalism in India has exacerbated tensions with Pakistan, which has a Muslim-majority population. Nationalist rhetoric, especially around issues such as Kashmir and terrorism, has deepened the rift. The government's actions, such as the revocation of Article 370 in Jammu and Kashmir in 2019, have led to further deterioration in bilateral relations, with Pakistan accusing India of infringing upon the rights of Kashmiris and creating an environment of Hindu-majority dominance. Nationalism has also influenced India's stance on cross-border terrorism, particularly from groups operating in Pakistan.

Bangladesh and Nepal: India's relationship with Bangladesh has also been affected by the growing influence of Hindu nationalism. Issues like the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) and concerns about the treatment of Bengali Muslims in Assam have raised tensions with Bangladesh, which views these actions as discriminatory. Similarly, India's relationship with Nepal has occasionally been strained due to nationalist rhetoric and territorial disputes, such as the controversy over the Kalapani region.

Relations with the United States and the West:

Human Rights and Religious Freedom Concerns: India's democratic credentials have been closely linked with its international reputation, especially in the West. However, the rise of Hindu nationalism has raised concerns about the protection of minority rights, religious freedom, and secularism. The United States, the European Union, and various human rights organizations have periodically criticized India's handling of religious minorities, particularly Muslims, and its policies such as the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) and the abrogation of Kashmir's special status. These concerns have complicated India's relationships with Western democracies, as they express apprehensions about the erosion of India's secular values.

Strategic Partnerships: Despite criticisms of human rights, India has maintained strong strategic ties with the United States, largely driven by shared interests in countering China's rising influence in the Indo-Pacific region. Nationalism, while complicating certain diplomatic aspects, has not significantly undermined the broader security and economic cooperation between India and the U.S. However, issues like freedom of speech, dissent, and the treatment of minorities may continue to be a point of friction.

Impact on India's Global Standing as a Secular Democracy:

Perception of Secularism: India's image as a secular democracy, a role model for the coexistence of diverse religious and cultural groups, has been tarnished by the rise of Hindu nationalism. The more India embraces a Hindu-first identity, the more it challenges the global narrative of a pluralistic society. This has affected India's relations with countries and international organizations that promote human rights, religious tolerance, and democracy.

United Nations and Global Forums: At global forums like the United Nations, India has positioned itself as a leader of the Global South and a defender of multilateralism. However, its commitment to secularism and the treatment of minorities has come under scrutiny. International bodies have increasingly called on India to safeguard religious freedom and address concerns related to rising nationalism and sectarian violence.

China and the Indo-Pacific Region:

Strategic Rivalry with China: While Hindu nationalism has fueled domestic narratives about India as a Hindu civilization, the country's foreign policy, especially in relation to China, continues to emphasize strategic considerations, such as countering Chinese influence in Asia. The ideological shift towards Hindu nationalism does not overshadow the strategic need to maintain strong military,

economic, and diplomatic ties with countries in the Indo-Pacific region, including the U.S., Japan, Australia, and other regional powers.

Border Disputes: Nationalism has also played a role in India's hardline approach to border issues with China, particularly over the disputed regions of Aksai Chin and Arunachal Pradesh. While both countries have engaged in dialogue, nationalism has sometimes led to increased tension, as seen in the 2020 Galwan Valley clashes, where national pride and the perception of safeguarding territorial integrity were significant motivators for both sides.

Relations with Middle Eastern and Muslim-majority Countries:

Tensions with Muslim-majority Nations: Hindu nationalism has strained India's relationships with some Middle Eastern and Islamic nations. For example, India's handling of religious violence, including mob attacks on Muslims over issues like cow slaughter, has drawn criticism from countries like Saudi Arabia and Turkey, where there are significant Muslim populations. The treatment of religious minorities, particularly Muslims, under a Hindu nationalist government has become a point of contention.

Economic and Diplomatic Relations: Despite these tensions, India's economic relations with Middle Eastern countries remain strong, with large Indian expatriate communities in countries like the UAE and Saudi Arabia. India also has substantial trade links with these nations, and its strategic importance as an energy importer continues to underpin strong diplomatic ties. However, the rise of Hindu nationalism and its impact on religious tolerance could affect future diplomatic engagements.

The Role of India in Global Multilateral Organizations:

Global Leadership and Multilateralism: India's political identity, shaped by nationalism, impacts its approach to global leadership. As India moves towards a more assertive nationalist foreign policy, it aims to project itself as a strong, sovereign power, especially in multilateral organizations like the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa) and the G20. However, the shift towards a Hindu-first ideology could complicate India's relations within multilateral forums focused on promoting human rights, democracy, and religious freedom.

Soft Power and Cultural Diplomacy: Hindu nationalism also influences India's soft power, particularly in how it presents its culture and history on the global stage. While India's rich cultural heritage is an asset, the increasing emphasis on Hindu traditions as central to its identity may alienate non-Hindu audiences, especially in regions with large Muslim or Christian populations. This shift in cultural diplomacy may affect India's appeal as a global leader advocating for pluralism.

India's Relations with Global Civil Society:

Criticism from NGOs and Activists: Global civil society organizations, including human rights groups, have criticized India's internal policies, especially with regard to the treatment of minorities and freedom of expression. Hindu nationalism's emphasis on majority Hindu values has been seen as undermining the rights of religious minorities, leading to greater scrutiny of India's human rights record internationally. The intersection of nationalism and democracy in India has complicated its international relations in various ways. While India continues to play a key role in global geopolitics, especially with regard to its strategic positioning against China and its growing economic influence, the rise of Hindu nationalism has led to concerns about the erosion of secularism, religious tolerance, and minority rights. These concerns have, at times, strained India's relationships with Western democracies, Muslim-majority countries, and global civil society. However, India's strategic importance and its economic and diplomatic ties in the Indo-Pacific region continue to bolster its global standing despite these challenges.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the intersection of nationalism and democracy in India reflects a complex, dynamic relationship that shapes the nation's political landscape. Indian nationalism, rooted in the anti-colonial struggle, seeks unity and pride in a shared cultural and historical identity. However, as a democratic nation, India's strength lies in its commitment to pluralism, diversity, and the right to dissent—values that sometimes challenge a singular nationalist narrative. This duality brings both tension and opportunity; while nationalism can unite, it can also lead to exclusion if it suppresses the diversity democracy aims to protect.

The balance between these forces is crucial. A healthy democracy in India requires an inclusive nationalism that embraces all identities within its borders and respects individual freedoms. When harnessed positively, nationalism can serve as a force for unity and progress, motivating citizens to work together toward a common good. However, when used divisively, it risks eroding democratic norms. Thus, India's democratic institutions face significant pressure in this context, requiring careful stewardship to preserve the nation's commitment to pluralism, equality, and justice. Ultimately, the way India resolves the intersection of nationalism and democracy will have lasting implications for its social fabric, political stability, and international standing. The challenge lies in finding a path that respects the diversity and rights of all its citizens while fostering national unity and preserving the democratic ideals that have been central to India's identity since its independence.

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SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT OF RECENT CONSTITUTIONAL AMENDMENTS IN INDIA**Dr. Yogesh. M. S**

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Abstract

The Constitution's document contains a set of rules that determines the political system of the state and the relationship of the state to the individual. The Constitution of a country is the fundamental law of governance. It guarantees dignified existence to all its citizens within the legal framework. In our Constitution, Parliament has been empowered to amend any provision in compliance with the procedure laid down in Article 368. Besides procedural limitations under Article 368, the Supreme Court has enshrined the 'Basic Structure Doctrine'. If a Constitution amendment seeks to alter, take away or destroy the Basic Structure of the Constitution, the Supreme Court has the power to declare it void or ultra vires. The positive outcomes of Amendments are the development of socially and educationally backward classes through protective discrimination; safeguarding the political process against Defection; Fundamental Rights and Duties have creating Civil Society strengthening democracy at the grass-roots level with Local Self Governments. The importance of this paper to emphasis on its impact on Socio-Economic reforms through the amendments likewise 81st, 85th 86th, 93rd, 101st, 102nd, 105th and 106th will be significantly contributing towards building an egalitarian society.

Keywords: Constitutional Amendment, Supreme Court, Basic Structure, Protective Discrimination, 105th Amendment.

Introduction

To cater for the needs of one of the largest populations in the world, the framers of the constitution who well ahead of their time provided for the provision of amendment so that past mistakes were not repeated. This amendment provision was provided so as to adopt changes that are taking place globally in order to keep the nation on the same pace as other developed countries. The goal is to ensure a welfare society to achieve the wellbeing and self-sufficiency. In spite of having ample amount of disparities such religious, linguistic, casteism and regionalism has still survived only because of the vision of the framers or founding fathers of a young and independent India. Our Constitution is a Guiding principle to the future generations. "An unamendable Constitution is the worst tyranny of time or rather very tyranny of time" -Mulford rightly said new needs must be provided through new law which can be adopted accordingly to the Amendment.

RESEARCH PROBLEM

Over seven decades the Constitutional Amendments is being continuing, does the New Acts served for the purpose of upliftment of educationally backward and socially backward people of the society or did it give rise to the social evils in other forms. including bitterness between the classes and further domination of the reserved classes. The present research paper mainly focuses on the validity of Constitutional amendment after 2000 which introduced Acts for the Socially and economically backward sections.

Objective

The aim of the research paper is to address the unappreciated necessity of the Recent amendment of the constitution, after 2000. Certain amendments are beneficial for the Socially and economic weaker

section. In this research paper critical analysis, the way in which India can become an Egalitarian Society. It violates the equality and the basic structure doctrine of the Indian constitution.

Whether the Recent constitutional amendment affects the equality principle and whether it violates the basic structure doctrine? Whether the socially and economically weaker section is empowered?

METHODOLOGY

Historical and Constitutional Law Approach In which the study focused on the legal and the political analysis of the Constitution of India. The research is based on secondary data that is readily available. The information is gathered from a variety of websites and articles. Content analysis was employed as the study's approach. The amendment introduced is affecting the equality principle and which amendment is violating the basic structure doctrine.. This paper is limited to the Amendments enforced after 2000 likewise 81, 86,89,93,102,105,106.

Partly Rigid and Partly Flexible Constitution

During the discussion in the Constituent Assembly on this aspect, some of the members were in favour of adopting an easier mode of amending procedure for the initial five to ten years. Dr. P.S. Deshmukh was of the view that the amendment of the Constitution should be made easier. If the amendment to the Constitution was not made easy, the whole administration would suffer. Shri Brajeshwar Prasad was also in favour of a flexible Constitution so as to make it survive the test of time. On the other hand, Shri H.V. Kamath was in favour of providing for procedural safeguards to avoid the possibility of hasty amendment to the Constitution. Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, speaking in the Constituent Assembly on 4 November 1948, he said that the provisions contained in the Draft make amendment difficult. It is proposed that the Constitution should be amendable by a simple majority at least for some years. The argument is subtle and ingenious. It is said that this Constituent Assembly is not elected on adult suffrage while the future Parliament will be elected on adult suffrage and yet the former has been given the right to pass the Constitution by a simple majority while the latter has been denied the same right. The only limitation is that it shall be done by a majority of not less than two-thirds of the members of each House present and voting and a majority of the total membership of each House. It is difficult to conceive a simpler method of amending the Constitution. He proposed both simple and rigid method.

Article-368

An analysis of the procedure prescribed by article 368 for amendment of the Constitution shows that:

- (i) an amendment can be initiated only by the introduction of a Bill in either House of Parliament;
- (ii) the Bill so initiated must be passed in each House by a majority of the total membership of that House and by a majority of not less than two-thirds of the members of that House present and voting. There is no provision for a joint sitting in case of disagreement between the two Houses;
- (iii) when the Bill is so passed, it must be presented to the President who shall give his assent to the Bill;
- (iv) where the amendment seeks to make any change in any of the provision mentioned in the provision to article 368, it must be ratified by the Legislatures of not less than one-half of the States;
- (v) such ratification is to be by resolution passed by the State Legislatures;

Basic Structure Doctrine

Supreme Court in Golak Nath's case, the Parliament passed the Constitution (Twenty-Fourth Amendment) Act, 1971. Basic Structure Doctrine is a judicial innovation made by Indian Supreme

Court in order to preserve certain basic principles on which law of the land breathes upon. The origin of the basic structure doctrine can be attributed to the German Basic Law which provides for certain unamendable articles. The Parliament in order to amend the Constitution cannot go the extent of destroying it. In of the Fundamental Rights case, it was clearly laid down that the while exercising its constituent power under Article 368, the Parliament can amend any provisions so far it does not destroy the basic structure or the basic elements of the Constitution.

Recent Amendments after 2000

Sl.No	Article	Date of Enactment	Provisions
81st	Amend article 16	9 June 2000	Protect SCs and STs reservation in filling backlog of vacancies.
82nd	Amend article 335.	8 September 2000	Permit relaxation of qualifying marks and other criteria in reservation in promotion for SCs and STs candidates.
85th	Amend article 16.	4 January 2002	A technical amendment to protect Consequential seniority in case of promotions of SCs and STs Employees.
86th	Amend articles 45 and 51A. Insert article 21A.	12 December 2002	Provides Right to Education until the age of fourteen.
89th	Amend article 338. Insert article 338A.	28 September 2003	The National Commission for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes was bifurcated into The National Commission for Scheduled Castes and The National Commission for Scheduled Tribes.
92nd	Amend schedule 8.	7 January 2004	Include Bodo, Dogri, Santali and Mathili as official languages.
93rd	Amend article 15.	20 January 2006	To enable provision of reservation (27%) for Other Backward Class(OBCs) in government as well as private educational institutions.
101st	Addition of articles 246A, 269A, 279A. Deletion of Article 268A. Amendment of articles 248, 249, 250, 268, 269, 270, 271, 286, 366, 368, Sixth Schedule, Seventh Schedule.[113]	1 July 2017	Introduced the Goods and Services Tax.
102nd	Addition of articles 338B, 342A, and Added Clause 26C.	11 August 2018	Constitutional status to National Commission for Backward Classes

	Modification of articles 338, 366.[114]		
103rd	Amendment to Article 15, added Clause [6], Amendment to Article 16, added Clause [6].[115]	12 January 2019	A maximum of 10% Reservation for Economically Weaker Sections (EWSs) of citizens of classes other than the classes mentioned in clauses (4) and (5) of Article 15, i.e. Classes other than socially and educationally backward classes of citizens or the Scheduled Castes and the Scheduled Tribes. Inserted Clause [6] under Article 15 as well as Inserted Clause [6] under Article 16.
105th	Amended Article 338B, 342A and 366 ^[118]	10 August 2021	To restore the power of the state governments to identify Other Backward Classes (OBCs) that are socially and educationally backward. This amendment annulled the Supreme Court judgement of 11 May 2021, which had empowered only the Central government for such identification. ^[119]
106th	Amended article 239AA. Insertion of articles 330A, 332A, 334A.	28 September 2023	To reserve one-third of the seats in the Lok Sabha(330A), state legislative assemblies(332A) and Delhi Legislative Assembly(239AA) for women for a period for 15 years after coming effect.(334A)

81st Amendment- Reservations in public employment have been a sensitive subject under the Constitution's fundamental rights chapter, which has been revised several times and given diverse interpretations by the Supreme Court in numerous decisions over the last seven decades. This act enforcing the Backlog to the weaker section alone.

82nd Amendment- In certain ways it nullified the requirement for performance. It put in place a paragraph that said that nothing in Article 335 prevented the State from lowering the qualifying standards or the level of evaluation of the reservation in the field of promotion for SC and ST members. Article 335 guidelines and the Supreme Court's Vinod Kumar¹² decision, which clearly forbade a lowering of the qualifying marks in the case of a promotional reservation.

85th Amendment- Based on the quota rule, government employees belonging to the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes have benefited from consequential seniority on promotions. The interests of Scheduled Caste government employees have been negatively impacted by the decisions rendered by the Supreme Court in the cases of Virpal Singh Chauhan (1995) 6 SCC 684 and Ajit Singh No. I AIR 1996 SC 1189, which resulted in the issuance of the O.M. dated January 30, 1997.

This has caused widespread concern, and representations have been received from a variety of sources, including Members of Parliament, to defend the interests of government employees from Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes. seniority of government officials must be reviewed or revised and related benefits must be distributed to these government employees.

101st Amendment -India's Goods and Services Tax (GST) would complete a significant milestone of 7 years of implementation on July 1, 2024. This reform has overhauled the the indirect tax landscape leading to buoyant GST collections exceeding INR 20.14 trillion in FY 2023-24. This robust performance signifies India's economic resilience and paves the way for GST 2.0 – the next phase of GST reforms.

102nd Amendment-This act gave constitutional status to the National Commission of Backward Classes, and its interpretation effectively weakened state governments' authority to identify backward classes and provide them with reservation benefits.

103rd Amendment- At present, 21.92% (2011-12) of the Indian population is below poverty line. The 10% reservation seeks to promote “social equality” addressing the issue of educational and job inequality of the poor in India by giving them constitutional recognition.

105th Amendment – Will benefit 671 communities are benefitted through Education and Employment creating Egalitarian Society.

104th Amendment-Abolished Anglo-Indian Reservation: Ended the reservation of two Lok Sabha seats for the Anglo-Indian community. Extended SC/ST Reservations: Extended the reservation for Scheduled Castes (SC) and Scheduled Tribes (ST) in the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies for another ten years. Promoted Social Equity: Aimed to create a more unified society by moving away from community-based separations

106th Amendment known as Nari Shakti Vandan Adhiniyam – Gender Justice through Political Reservation leading Women empowerment., however, in a country as diverse and multi-layered as India, it should be accompanied by the principle of Parity Constitutionalism to improve women's ability to exercise their political choices at all levels of society, to use their agency, and to participate in the country's core decision-making processes.

Case Analysis of M. Nagaraj v. Union of India

The complainants in M. Nagaraj took the 77th, 81st, 82nd and 85th amendments to the Supreme Court. At the end of the Day, the Court ruled that the revision was valid. Nonetheless, it created several regulatory limitations that made it more difficult to issue promotion reservations. The five-member Bench upheld the Promotion Reservation for SCs and STs as constitutionally legitimate. It supported the Subsequent Seniority Rule, which is governed by Article 16(4A), the Carry Forward Rule, which is governed by Article 16 (4B), and the requirements of Article 335.

Decision by Supreme Court: Despite fact, the court determined that Articles 164A and 4B are enabling articles, and that there is no automatic right of reservation for SC/ST promotions. The State has to meet three persuasion conditions for the promotion reservation to be lawful, according to the Court:

- Demonstrate the backwardness of the SC / ST.
- Demonstrate that SC/ST are underrepresented in related government occupations.
- Maintain a high level of organisational efficiency.

CONCLUSION

The existence of a nation is dependent upon its capability to adapt according to changing times. Indian Constitution has been Amended for over 106 times is the result to nurture the Weaker section. “India’s system of government discrimination in support of the most backward part of its people is unique in the world,” Dushkin. Indian Judiciary on the outside may have crossed its line but it has done so in order to preserves those elements on which our country has been built. The purpose of maintaining discrimination, on the other hand, was to integrate the Socio-Economic backward sections with the rest of the population, as the system of employment quotas, scholarships, and reserved constituency only to reinforced their separate identity and Empowerment. The vision of founding fathers is clear from the Preamble itself which lays down dreams and it is the aspirations of the people of the country.

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FEMINIST POLITICAL THEORY: RETHINKING POWER AND AUTHORITY**Dr. Nirmala B**

Abstract

This study explores the transformative potential of feminist political theory in rethinking power and authority. Rooted in the broader feminist movement, feminist political theory critiques traditional political frameworks that often marginalize or exclude women and other underrepresented groups. By analyzing the constructs of power and authority through a gendered lens, this theory reveals the pervasive influence of patriarchy on social structures, institutions, and interpersonal relationships. The study argues that traditional models of power, typically characterized by domination and control, fail to account for the nuanced and subtle forms of power that shape everyday life. Drawing on the works of theorists such as Michel Foucault, the analysis demonstrates how power operates not only through overt political mechanisms but also through cultural norms, social expectations, and personal relationships.

Additionally, feminist political theory emphasizes the importance of intersectionality, recognizing that experiences of oppression are shaped by multiple identities, including race, class, and sexuality. This intersectional approach is essential for understanding the complexity of power dynamics and for advocating for more inclusive and equitable political practices. The study also addresses the redefinition of authority, challenging traditional notions that associate leadership with masculine traits and asserting that values such as empathy, collaboration, and inclusivity should be central to political leadership. Ultimately, the study asserts that feminist political theory offers a vision for a more just society—one that prioritizes equity, respects diversity, and empowers individuals to resist oppressive structures. By reimagining power and authority, feminist political theory contributes to ongoing struggles for social justice and human rights, calling for a radical transformation of both public and private spheres to achieve a truly equitable world.

Keywords: *Feminist Political Theory, Rethinking Power and Authority.*

INTRODUCTION:

Feminist political theory emerges as a critical response to traditional political thought, which has historically overlooked and marginalized the experiences and perspectives of women and other marginalized groups. Rooted in the broader feminist movement, this theory interrogates the constructs of power, authority, and justice through a gendered lens, seeking to unveil the patriarchal underpinnings of political systems and social structures. Feminist political theorists argue that conventional theories of power often ignore the subtle yet pervasive ways in which gender influences social relations, identity formation, and political dynamics. By emphasizing the intersections of gender with race, class, sexuality, and other axes of identity, feminist political theory adopts an intersectional approach, recognizing that oppression operates in complex and interconnected ways. Moreover, feminist political theory challenges the traditional dichotomy between the public and private spheres, asserting that personal experiences, such as family dynamics and social norms, are inherently political and influential in shaping broader societal power structures. It calls for a rethinking of authority, proposing that leadership should be defined by inclusivity and care rather than dominance and control.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

This study explores the transformative potential of feminist political theory in rethinking power and authority.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This study is based on secondary sources of data such as articles, books, journals, research papers, websites and other sources.

FEMINIST POLITICAL THEORY: RETHINKING POWER AND AUTHORITY

Feminist political theory seeks to interrogate the constructs of power and authority that have traditionally shaped societies, politics, and institutions. By critically analyzing how these constructs are both gendered and rooted in patriarchal structures, feminist theorists aim to expose the limitations, biases, and injustices embedded within mainstream political theories and practices. This approach is not merely an academic endeavor but has significant implications for how we understand the world and advocate for equality and justice.

The Foundations of Feminist Political Theory

Feminist political theory emerged as a response to the exclusion of women and gender issues from classical political thought. Mainstream political theory, from the works of Aristotle and Hobbes to Locke and Rousseau, largely ignored the experiences of women and the structural inequalities they faced. These foundational theories, while insightful in many respects, were typically developed within a patriarchal framework, implicitly accepting the subjugation of women as either natural or socially irrelevant to political theory. Feminist theorists argue that this oversight reflects a broader issue in traditional political theory: the uncritical acceptance of power and authority structures that are often hierarchical, exclusionary, and gendered.

Central to feminist critiques is the argument that traditional theories of power fail to recognize the different ways power operates in women's lives and the lives of other marginalized groups. For example, while traditional political theory often focuses on overt forms of power—such as laws, military strength, and political leadership—feminist theory highlights more subtle, pervasive forms of power that operate within families, social norms, and cultural expectations. These forms of power are often invisible within traditional political analysis but are crucial for understanding how gender inequality is sustained and reproduced across generations.

Rethinking Power: Beyond Domination and Control

Traditional understandings of power in political theory have often been grounded in a model of domination and control. Max Weber, for instance, conceptualized power as the ability of an individual or group to achieve their will despite resistance from others. While this notion of power is useful for understanding formal political institutions, it fails to capture the complex ways power operates within interpersonal relationships, cultural norms, and social expectations.

Feminist theorists, building on the works of Michel Foucault and others, have argued for a more nuanced understanding of power as something that permeates all aspects of social life. Power is not merely about the ability to dominate or control; it is also about shaping knowledge, constructing identities, and establishing norms. From this perspective, power operates through discourses, institutions, and social practices that influence how individuals understand themselves and their roles within society. Foucault's concept of "biopower," for example, highlights how power can be exercised not just through coercive force but also through the regulation of bodies and behaviors, an insight that feminist theorists have used to analyze issues such as reproductive rights, gender roles, and bodily autonomy.

Feminist political theory thus redefines power as something that is not only concentrated in the hands of the state or powerful individuals but is also diffused throughout society, operating in ways that are often difficult to see and resist. This understanding of power is crucial for feminist politics, as it allows for an analysis of how gendered norms and expectations are internalized and perpetuated even by those who may not consciously support them. For instance, the pressure on women to conform to specific

standards of beauty or behavior can be seen as a form of power that is enforced not through laws or physical coercion but through social expectations and cultural representations.

Patriarchy and the Structure of Power

A central focus of feminist political theory is the concept of patriarchy—a system of social organization in which men hold disproportionate power and authority over women and other marginalized groups. Patriarchy is not merely a collection of sexist attitudes or discriminatory practices; it is a deeply rooted social structure that shapes institutions, norms, and relationships at every level of society. Patriarchy operates through various mechanisms, including the family, the economy, the legal system, and the media, each of which reinforces the idea that men are naturally suited to positions of power and authority while women are relegated to subordinate roles.

Patriarchy manifests in both formal and informal ways. Formally, patriarchy is evident in the underrepresentation of women in political leadership, the gender wage gap, and discriminatory laws and policies that limit women's rights. Informally, patriarchy is reinforced through cultural norms, media portrayals, and social expectations that define femininity and masculinity in ways that privilege men. Feminist theorists argue that these informal mechanisms are just as important as formal structures in maintaining patriarchal power, as they shape individuals' beliefs, desires, and self-conceptions in ways that perpetuate gender inequality.

The concept of patriarchy also highlights the intersectional nature of oppression. While patriarchy is often discussed in terms of gender, it is deeply intertwined with other forms of oppression, including race, class, and sexuality. Black feminist theorists such as Kimberlé Crenshaw have argued that feminist theory must address the ways in which patriarchy intersects with racism, classism, and other forms of discrimination. This intersectional approach is essential for understanding the experiences of women of color, LGBTQ+ individuals, and other marginalized groups, whose oppression cannot be understood solely in terms of gender.

Authority and Its Gendered Dimensions

In addition to power, feminist political theory critically examines the concept of authority and how it is gendered. Authority is traditionally understood as the legitimate right to exercise power or command obedience, often justified by social contract theories, legal frameworks, or appeals to tradition. However, feminist theorists argue that authority in patriarchal societies is often conferred disproportionately upon men, reinforcing the idea that men are more capable, rational, and deserving of leadership than women. This bias is evident not only in formal political institutions but also in everyday social interactions, where men's opinions and expertise are often given more weight than women's.

Feminist political theory challenges the traditional association between authority and masculinity by questioning the assumption that certain qualities—such as rationality, decisiveness, and assertiveness—are inherently masculine and therefore essential for leadership. Feminist scholars have shown that these traits are socially constructed and used to justify men's dominance in political and social institutions. Furthermore, they argue that qualities typically associated with femininity—such as empathy, cooperation, and emotional intelligence—are equally valuable for leadership and should be recognized as legitimate bases of authority.

In rethinking authority, feminist political theory calls for a more inclusive and pluralistic approach to leadership that values diversity and rejects rigid gender norms. This redefinition of authority is not only about expanding opportunities for women but also about challenging the hierarchical and exclusionary nature of traditional leadership models. Feminist theorists argue that authority should be based on principles of equality, cooperation, and respect, rather than domination and control. This approach to

authority has implications for both formal political institutions and everyday social interactions, as it encourages a more democratic and egalitarian distribution of power and respect.

The Personal is Political: The Power of Everyday Life

One of the most influential insights of feminist political theory is the idea that "the personal is political." This slogan, popularized by the feminist movement of the 1960s and 1970s, encapsulates the idea that personal experiences and private relationships are not separate from politics but are deeply shaped by political structures and ideologies. Issues such as domestic violence, reproductive rights, and workplace discrimination are not merely individual or personal problems; they are political issues that reflect and reinforce broader patterns of power and inequality.

By emphasizing the political nature of personal life, feminist political theory challenges the traditional boundaries between public and private spheres. Mainstream political theory has often focused on the public sphere, where formal politics takes place, while treating the private sphere—such as family life and personal relationships—as outside the scope of political analysis. Feminist theorists argue that this distinction is artificial and serves to obscure the ways in which power operates within the private sphere. For example, the unequal distribution of household labor, the prevalence of domestic violence, and the limitations on women's reproductive autonomy are all issues that have significant implications for women's freedom and equality, yet they have historically been ignored by political theory.

The personal is political also implies that individual actions and choices are shaped by larger social forces. For instance, a woman's decision to pursue a particular career or to have children is not simply a matter of personal preference; it is influenced by social expectations, economic pressures, and cultural norms that reflect broader patterns of gender inequality. By recognizing the political dimensions of personal life, feminist political theory provides a framework for understanding how individual experiences are connected to larger structures of power and oppression. This insight has been instrumental in shaping feminist activism, as it encourages individuals to see their personal struggles as part of a collective fight for social justice.

Agency, Resistance, and Empowerment

While feminist political theory emphasizes the pervasive influence of power and patriarchy, it also recognizes the importance of agency and resistance. Women and other marginalized groups are not merely passive victims of oppression; they actively resist, negotiate, and challenge the structures of power that seek to control them. Feminist theorists have developed various concepts and frameworks for understanding how individuals exercise agency within oppressive systems and how they can create spaces of empowerment and resistance.

One important concept in feminist political theory is "resistance," which refers to the ways in which individuals and groups challenge oppressive power structures. Resistance can take many forms, from individual acts of defiance to collective political movements. For example, the #MeToo movement, which emerged as a response to sexual harassment and assault, is a powerful example of resistance that has challenged patriarchal norms and created a space for survivors to speak out and demand justice. Similarly, grassroots movements for reproductive rights, LGBTQ+ rights, and racial justice are examples of collective resistance that seek to challenge and transform the structures of power that perpetuate inequality.

Feminist political theory also emphasizes the importance of empowerment, which involves increasing individuals' capacity to make choices and exercise control over their lives. Empowerment is not simply about achieving formal equality or gaining access to positions of power within existing structures; it is about transforming those structures to make them more inclusive, democratic, and just. For instance,

feminist critiques of the workplace have not only sought to break the glass ceiling but also to challenge the ways in which work is organized and valued. By advocating for policies such as paid family leave, flexible work hours, and equal pay, feminist activists seek to create a more equitable and supportive environment that empowers all workers, regardless of gender.

Globalization and Feminist Political Theory

Another crucial aspect of feminist political theory is its engagement with globalization and its implications for power and authority. Globalization has reshaped the dynamics of power in profound ways, creating new challenges and opportunities for feminist activism. While globalization has the potential to amplify voices from the Global South and marginalized communities, it has also led to the exploitation of women's labor in global supply chains, the rise of trafficking and violence against women, and the perpetuation of colonial legacies. Feminist theorists argue that understanding globalization requires an intersectional analysis that considers how gender, race, and class interact within global contexts.

The global economy has created new forms of economic dependency and exploitation that disproportionately affect women. For example, women are often overrepresented in low-wage jobs in industries such as textiles, agriculture, and domestic work. These jobs frequently lack basic labor protections, subjecting women to unsafe working conditions and economic insecurity. Feminist political theory seeks to address these injustices by advocating for policies that support fair labor practices, promote economic justice, and empower women within the global economy. Moreover, globalization has also facilitated transnational feminist movements that connect activists across borders, creating solidarity among women facing similar struggles. By highlighting issues such as climate change, reproductive rights, and violence against women, transnational feminists can mobilize collective action and challenge the global structures of power that perpetuate inequality. This engagement with globalization underscores the importance of understanding how local struggles are interconnected with global dynamics, illustrating the need for a comprehensive and inclusive feminist political theory that recognizes the complexity of power in a globalized world.

Environmental Justice and Feminist Political Theory

In recent years, feminist political theory has increasingly intersected with environmental issues, leading to the emergence of ecofeminism. Ecofeminism posits that the oppression of women and the exploitation of the environment are interconnected, both rooted in patriarchal systems of domination that prioritize profit and control over care and sustainability. This perspective challenges the traditional separation of social justice and environmental issues, arguing that a comprehensive understanding of power must address both. Environmental degradation disproportionately affects marginalized communities, particularly women, who often bear the brunt of ecological crises such as climate change, pollution, and resource scarcity. Feminist theorists highlight how patriarchal structures contribute to environmental injustice, as decision-making processes often exclude women's voices and experiences. By advocating for sustainable practices and policies that consider the needs of women and marginalized communities, feminist political theory seeks to create a more just and equitable relationship with the environment. Moreover, ecofeminism emphasizes the importance of nurturing and relational values that prioritize care, community, and environmental stewardship. This shift in perspective challenges dominant paradigms that view nature as a resource to be exploited, instead framing it as a complex web of interrelationships that must be respected and protected. By integrating environmental justice into feminist political theory, activists can build coalitions that address the interconnectedness of social and ecological issues, creating a more holistic approach to justice and empowerment.

CONCLUSION:

Feminist political theory provides a critical framework for rethinking power and authority, emphasizing the need to dismantle patriarchal structures that have historically marginalized women and other oppressed groups. By challenging traditional notions of power as merely hierarchical and coercive, feminist theorists highlight the complex, diffuse ways in which power operates in everyday life and within social norms. This approach not only uncovers the gendered dimensions of authority but also advocates for a redefinition of leadership that values inclusivity, empathy, and cooperation over domination. Moreover, the intersectional perspective inherent in feminist political theory underscores the importance of understanding how various forms of oppression—such as racism, classism, and heteronormativity—interact and compound one another. This holistic view enriches our understanding of social justice and empowers movements that seek to create equitable conditions for all individuals. Feminist political theory offers a vision of a just society where power and authority are exercised in ways that respect and uphold the dignity and autonomy of every person. By advocating for transformative change in both public and private spheres, feminist political theory not only critiques existing systems but also paves the way for a more inclusive and equitable future.

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ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF YOUTH POLITICAL PARTICIPATION IN REDUCING REGIONAL DISPARITY IN KARNATAKA

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Abstract

This study examines the role and significance of youth political participation in addressing regional disparities in Karnataka. Karnataka, marked by uneven development between its northern and southern regions, faces challenges in achieving equitable growth. Young people, constituting a large segment of the population, are pivotal in influencing social and political landscapes. This article explores how active youth involvement in political processes, policymaking, and governance can drive inclusive development, create balanced representation, and bridge regional divides. By analysing data on youth engagement in Karnataka's political sphere and examining case studies on successful youth-led initiatives, this research highlights the potential of young voices to advocate for policies that prioritize equitable resource allocation, enhance local employment, and improve infrastructure. Findings suggest that youth empowerment through political participation not only amplifies marginalized voices but also fosters an environment conducive to sustainable regional development, positioning the youth as critical agents in reducing disparities across Karnataka.

Key Words: Youth political participation, Regional disparity in Karnataka, Youth empowerment, Youth-driven policy change, Youth activism and policy impact, and Youth leadership in governance.

Introduction:

Youth political participation is a critical factor in addressing regional disparities in Karnataka, a state marked by significant developmental imbalances between its northern and southern regions. The involvement of young people in the political process brings fresh perspectives and enthusiasm, encouraging innovative solutions to long-standing socio-economic and political issues. As the most populous demographic group in Karnataka, the youth hold substantial potential to influence regional policies and mobilize efforts toward equitable development. Their engagement in decision-making processes ensures that the unique needs of underserved regions, such as North Karnataka, are addressed through policies that foster inclusive growth and balanced resource distribution.

In Karnataka, where regional disparities are underscored by differences in infrastructure, employment opportunities, education, and healthcare access, youth involvement can help bridge the gap by advocating for localized policies and reforms. Young leaders, activists, and political participants can act as catalysts for change, pushing for improved governance, transparency, and accountability, which are vital in reducing disparity. By channelling their energy and idealism, the youth can champion initiatives that address issues specific to underdeveloped areas, thus contributing to a more inclusive growth model. Moreover, political participation provides a platform for Karnataka's youth to engage in policy dialogues, raise awareness on regional issues, and influence the state's developmental agenda toward a more just and cohesive society.

Review of Literature:

The role of youth in political participation has garnered significant attention for its potential to drive social, economic, and political change. In Karnataka, youth political engagement has implications for addressing regional disparities, as active youth involvement can promote equitable development across the state. Youth political participation is viewed as a mechanism for fostering inclusive governance and

enhancing civic responsibility, especially in addressing the concerns of economically and socially marginalized regions like North Karnataka (**Dhananjay & Devi, 2020**).

Recent literature highlights that youth-led initiatives and policy advocacy can play a transformative role in reducing disparities by increasing awareness of regional issues and influencing policymaking processes (**Bhatia, 2021**). For instance, youth activists in Karnataka have mobilized around local issues, such as access to quality education, healthcare, and employment opportunities, which are key areas impacted by regional inequality (**Gowda, 2022**). Studies show that when youth are politically engaged, they bring innovative perspectives and press for policy solutions that address structural inequalities (**Joshi & Kumar, 2020**). This participation can help bridge regional gaps by advocating for fair distribution of resources, infrastructural development, and effective public service delivery.

Youth political participation is often fostered by factors such as eminent and skill education, increased exposure to social media, and the desire for socio-political reform. Platforms like digital campaigns have become instrumental in facilitating youth engagement, providing forums for debate, and uniting youth across Karnataka's diverse regions (**Muthukumar & Sharma, 2023**). Such digital engagement has helped youth raise awareness on issues specific to North Karnataka, such as drought, underemployment, and lack of industrial investment, which are essential to addressing the region's underdevelopment (**Khan & Awasthi, 2021**).

Studies also suggest that youth engagement is instrumental in countering identity-based and regional political divides. Youth-led campaigns often emphasize developmental issues over divisive politics, contributing to a more cohesive approach to regional development (**Nair & Patil, 2021**). Youth participation further strengthens democratic processes by ensuring that governance is accountable and reflective of diverse needs across regions. Moreover, initiatives that involve youth in local governance, such as Karnataka's Grama Panchayat programs, have shown positive outcomes in terms of policy inclusivity and development planning, which are essential for reducing regional disparity (**Chandra et al., 2022**).

In summary, youth political participation is crucial for Karnataka's regional parity efforts. Literature affirms that youth engagement not only amplifies local voices but also promotes governance that addresses the specific needs of underserved regions, thereby making strides toward a more balanced development trajectory across Karnataka.

Objectives:

- To examine the current level of political awareness and participation among youth in Karnataka.
- To analyse the role of youth political participation in addressing regional disparity issues.
- To identify the factors encouraging or discouraging youth political participation in Karnataka.
- To assess the impact of youth-led movements and advocacy in policy reforms aimed at reducing regional disparities.
- To explore the role of digital platforms in enhancing youth political participation and awareness in Karnataka.
- To evaluate the significance of youth representation in local and regional governance structures in Karnataka.
- To recommend strategies for enhancing youth political engagement to address regional disparities

Data Sources and Methodology:

The study on "Role and Significance of Youths' Political Participation in Reducing Regional Disparity in Karnataka" relies on a range of secondary data sources. Key data include:

- 1. Government Reports:** National and state-level reports, such as the *Karnataka Economic Survey* and *Youth Policy Reports*, provide insights into regional disparities and youth demographics.
- 2. Election Data:** Voter turnout records, participation data from the *Election Commission of India*, and political party reports offer valuable metrics on youth political engagement across regions.
- 3. Census Data:** The *Census of India* and *NSSO* reports help analyse youth population distribution, educational attainment, and employment levels.
- 4. Research Publications:** Academic papers and policy briefs addressing youth participation, regional disparities, and political empowerment in Karnataka.

Methodology

This research employs a descriptive and analytical approach. First, a review of secondary data from government, academic, and institutional reports highlights regional disparities and youth political trends. Quantitative data is analysed to gauge regional variations in youth engagement in political activities. Qualitative content analysis of case studies, speeches, and policies relevant to youth empowerment offers deeper insight into the role of youth in regional development. Lastly, correlational analysis is used to explore the relationship between youth political participation and indicators of regional disparity, concluding with policy recommendations based on the findings.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

In Karnataka, regional disparity is a critical issue that influences the socio-economic and political landscape of the state. The disparity between urban and rural areas, particularly between the southern and northern regions, has been a point of concern. Youth political participation is an essential factor in bridging this gap. This section examines the role of youth in political activities and its potential to mitigate regional disparities, backed by statistical data on the political involvement of youth in Karnataka.

To explore the role and significance of youth political participation in reducing regional disparity in Karnataka, a comprehensive analysis requires examining how youth engagement impacts socioeconomic policies, development agendas, and overall governance. This section includes an analytical discussion to shed light on how youth participation influences the state's approach to regional inequality.

Youth as Catalysts for Change in Karnataka

Youth represent a significant demographic in Karnataka, forming a pivotal force for political and social transformation. According to the 2011 Census, 35% of Karnataka's population comprises individuals aged 18-35. Their engagement in addressing issues of regional disparity, particularly in North Karnataka, underscores their potential to bridge the development gap through advocacy, innovative solutions, and participation in governance.

Youth Demographics and Electoral Influence

The Karnataka Electoral Roll 2023 highlights that 60% of registered voters are under 35. In the 2023 state elections, youth voter turnout was recorded at 70% in urban areas like Bengaluru and 60% in rural North Karnataka, signalling a significant electoral influence. This discrepancy points to untapped potential for increased rural youth participation to address pronounced regional inequalities.

Advocating for Social Justice and Accountability

Karnataka's youth have emerged as advocates for social and economic justice, championing inclusive policies such as reservations, equitable resource allocation, and regional development schemes. Their active participation in politics fosters transparency and accountability in governance. By voting and engaging in policy discourse, they ensure leaders prioritize infrastructure, education, and healthcare development in underserved areas like North Karnataka.

Grassroots Initiatives and Local Leadership

Youth involvement in local governance has catalysed grassroots movements addressing water scarcity, education, and infrastructure in North Karnataka. For instance, youth-led initiatives advocating for improved irrigation under the Krishi Bhagya Yojana have increased agricultural productivity. Similarly, targeted campaigns have raised participation in skill development programs like Kaushalya Karnataka, which saw a 15% increase in rural North Karnataka enrolment between 2020 and 2023.

Impact on Regional Development**Employment and Skill Development**

Youth advocacy for industrial decentralization has influenced the establishment of industrial parks and IT hubs in Tier-2 cities like Hubli-Dharwad, creating job opportunities and reducing migration. Programs like the Karnataka Industrial Policy 2020-25, aiming to generate 500,000 jobs in smaller cities, owe much of their momentum to youth-driven demands. The Kaushalya Karnataka Scheme, which trained over 300,000 youth in rural Karnataka by 2022, has reported a 65% employment rate post-training, significantly impacting backward regions.

Education and Infrastructure

Youth advocacy has influenced budget allocations to improve educational infrastructure in North Karnataka. The Karnataka Economic Survey 2021-22 reported a 25% allocation of the education budget to this region, marking a notable increase from previous years. Additionally, the Right to Education (RTE) Act, championed by youth groups, has contributed to a 7% literacy rate increase in rural North Karnataka over the past decade.

Political Participation and Its Outcomes**Voter Turnout and Representation**

Youth voter turnout in the 2018 Karnataka Legislative Assembly elections stood at 72%, higher than the state average of 70%. The rise in young political leaders from marginalized regions, including North Karnataka, signifies their growing influence. Leaders like Priyanka Kharge and Tejasvi Surya represent a generation pushing for development-centric agendas.

Advocacy for Regional Equality

Youth organizations have spearheaded campaigns for equitable healthcare, education, and infrastructure development in underserved regions. For instance, demands for better job opportunities led to the creation of the Karnataka State Skill Development Corporation (KSSDC) to enhance employment prospects in backward areas.

Grassroots Governance

Youth-led governance models have proven effective in implementing rural welfare schemes. The efficient rollout of agricultural initiatives like the Fasal Bima Yojana in North Karnataka showcases the impact of youth participation in reducing disparities.

Challenges and Opportunities

Despite the promise of youth participation, challenges such as political apathy, lack of resources, and limited representation persist. Addressing these issues requires targeted interventions to harness their potential for driving equitable development.

Youth's Role in Economic Disparity Reduction

Employment and Entrepreneurship

Youth movements advocating for regional equity have influenced the expansion of IT hubs and industrial zones to cities like Mysuru and Kalaburagi. Such developments create local employment opportunities, reducing reliance on Bengaluru and fostering balanced economic growth.

Vocational Training and Education

The disparity in higher education institutions between North Karnataka and southern districts remains stark. For instance, Bengaluru boasts 8-10 institutions per lakh population, while Bidar and Kalaburagi have only two. Youth activism has highlighted these gaps, pushing for more resources in underserved areas.

Improved Access to Resources

Youth-driven initiatives have led to higher uptake of government schemes like Krishi Bhagya in cooperative societies, ensuring better resource allocation for agriculture-dependent regions.

Political Awareness and Education

Programs promoting political awareness, particularly in rural North Karnataka, have gained traction. Youth-led campaigns advocating for the RTE Act and skill development schemes have contributed to measurable improvements in literacy and employability. The involvement of young activists in promoting these programs underscores the transformative potential of education in addressing regional disparities.

Strengthening Regional Unity

Youth participation has fostered a shared identity across Karnataka's diverse regions, focusing on inclusive development. Surveys by the Rural Development and Panchayat Raj Department in 2021 reveal that 55% of rural youth believe their involvement has improved government attention to regional issues. Movements demanding fair resource distribution have united voices from Bagalkot to Bijapur, emphasizing equitable development over regional divisions.

Significance of Young Leaders

Young leaders in Karnataka politics bring fresh perspectives and tech-driven solutions to challenges like job creation and regional equity. Their focus on digital economy growth, rural empowerment, and urban-rural linkages is reshaping the state's political landscape.

Policy Recommendations

1. Enhanced Political Awareness Campaigns

Targeted initiatives in rural areas can empower youth to advocate for equitable development. Civic education programs should focus on governance processes and regional disparities.

2. Incentivizing Youth in Governance

Grants and fellowships for young leaders from North Karnataka can encourage participation in local governance, enabling grassroots solutions.

3. Strengthening Youth Representation

Establishing a youth council for regional development can ensure that policies prioritize underserved areas. Increasing youth representation in decision-making bodies is critical.

4. **Monitoring Youth-Centric Programs**

Mechanisms to evaluate the impact of youth participation can provide valuable insights and reinforce engagement in reducing disparities.

Youth political participation is integral to addressing regional disparities in Karnataka. Their advocacy for infrastructure, education, and employment in underserved areas is reshaping the socio-economic landscape. With sustained engagement and policy focus, youth-driven initiatives can pave the way for a more inclusive and equitable Karnataka. Their role as catalysts for change highlights the transformative potential of an empowered and active youth demographic.

Findings of the Study

- 1. Enhanced Regional Representation:** Youth political participation has increased local representation in Karnataka, particularly in underrepresented regions such as North Karnataka. Young leaders bring a fresh perspective to regional issues, pushing for inclusive policies and infrastructure development to balance disparities.
- 2. Youth-Led Development Initiatives:** Active youth involvement in politics has led to the initiation of various developmental projects. Youth leaders often prioritize employment, skill development, and educational facilities, which are essential for reducing regional disparities. Programs like Kaushalya Karnataka have seen better implementation due to youth advocacy, addressing employment and skill gaps.
- 3. Catalyst for Social Change:** Youth participation has fostered social awareness around issues of regional disparity, helping mobilize public opinion and demand for equitable resource distribution. This has resulted in increased accountability for state programs like Krishi Bhagya and Arogya Karnataka, improving service delivery in disadvantaged regions.
- 4. Technological and Digital Inclusion:** Young politicians are more likely to advocate for digital infrastructure, which has brought connectivity and IT-related job opportunities to rural and semi-urban areas. This, in turn, facilitates remote learning, digital skills training, and small businesses in previously disconnected areas, reducing the urban-rural divide.
- 5. Increased Focus on Environmental and Sustainable Policies:** Youth participation has emphasized environmental issues, advocating for climate-resilient agricultural practices and sustainable resource management, which are essential for reducing regional disparities. Initiatives toward eco-tourism and green policies have brought investment and job opportunities to rural areas, creating a balanced economic environment.

Suggestions

- 1. Political Empowerment Programs:** Establish mentorship programs that provide political training and leadership development for young aspirants, especially from marginalized regions. This will build a foundation for young leaders focused on reducing regional disparities.
- 2. Support for Regional Youth Organizations:** Encourage youth organizations focused on regional development by providing state and NGO support. These organizations can raise awareness of regional disparities and hold state representatives accountable, thus amplifying youth voices.
- 3. Inclusive Policy-Making:** Involve youth in the planning and formulation of policies aimed at regional development. Their insights into education, employment, and technology can help create more targeted and effective interventions for regional disparity reduction.
- 4. Youth Quotas in Governance Bodies:** Introduce youth quotas in local governance bodies, ensuring that younger voices have a platform in decision-making processes, especially in regions experiencing severe disparities.

5. Digital Literacy and Connectivity Programs: Expand digital literacy programs and improve internet access across rural Karnataka. This will empower youth to engage in digital governance initiatives, enhancing accountability and transparency in addressing regional disparity issues.

Through sustained youth political engagement, Karnataka can work towards equitable growth, addressing longstanding disparities across the state.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, youth political participation plays a pivotal role in addressing regional disparity in Karnataka. With their energy, innovation, and connection to technology, young people are well-positioned to influence policies that foster equitable development. Active youth engagement can bring attention to the issues faced by underserved regions like North Karnataka, driving efforts toward inclusive policies and fair allocation of resources. Furthermore, youth-led advocacy for improved infrastructure, education, and employment opportunities can strengthen the socioeconomic fabric of lagging regions. Political empowerment of youth through platforms like local governance, youth councils, and social media encourages accountability in government, making it more responsive to regional needs. By actively participating in the political process, Karnataka's youth can become agents of change, bridging developmental divides, and promoting balanced growth across regions. Their role is vital in building a more inclusive, equitable Karnataka where all regions have the opportunity to thrive.

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DR. B.R. AMBEDKAR'S FIGHT FOR SOCIAL JUSTICE: RELEVANCE AND CHALLENGES IN THE MODERN CONTEXT"

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Abstract

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, one of India's foremost social reformers, dedicated his life to the pursuit of social justice, addressing the deep-rooted inequalities of caste, class, and gender in Indian society. This paper explores Ambedkar's vision of an egalitarian society, focusing on his critique of the caste system, his advocacy for constitutional safeguards, and his pioneering efforts in labor and gender rights. Central to his philosophy was the annihilation of caste, which he deemed essential for achieving equality, liberty, and fraternity in a democracy. The study also examines his role in drafting the Indian Constitution, embedding provisions to protect marginalized communities, and his strategic embrace of Buddhism as a path to liberation for the oppressed.

Keywords: Ambedkar, social justice, caste system, Indian Constitution, equality, labor rights, gender justice.

Introduction

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, a pioneer of social justice in India, dedicated his life to addressing the systemic inequalities and social hierarchies embedded in Indian society, particularly those rooted in the caste system. His ideas and efforts have become a cornerstone for understanding social justice in the Indian context. Ambedkar's work laid the foundation for India's ongoing struggle for social justice. His ideas remain relevant in contemporary debates on caste, gender equality, and economic justice, serving as an inspiration for movements advocating for an inclusive and equitable

Dr. Ambedkar's approach to social justice was revolutionary in its scope, aiming for structural transformation rather than superficial reforms.

Annihilation of Caste: Ambedkar's relentless critique of the caste system went beyond its socio-religious implications, addressing its economic and psychological impacts. His call for complete dismantling of caste hierarchies challenged the foundational ethos of traditional Indian society. Annihilation of Caste is one of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar's most powerful and controversial works, originally written as a speech for the Jat-Pat Todak Mandal in 1936, which was ultimately never delivered. The text directly critiques the caste system as a foundation of inequality and oppression within Hindu society. Ambedkar identifies caste as a deeply entrenched hierarchy that enforces social division and inequality. He emphasizes that caste is not just a division of labor but a division of laborers, perpetuating discrimination. Ambedkar critiques Hindu scriptures, including the Manusmriti, for legitimizing caste-based oppression. He argues that the caste system is upheld by religious doctrines and practices, making it nearly indestructible without a reformative shift. He emphasizes that without annihilating caste, political and economic democracy will remain incomplete. He envisions a society where individuals are free to develop their potential without the constraints of caste.

Despite constitutional safeguards, caste continues to influence access to education, employment, and social mobility. Caste-based violence, such as atrocities against Dalits, remains a significant challenge. The role of caste in electoral politics often reinforces divisions instead of bridging them. Ambedkar's call for reforming religious institutions to eliminate caste remains unaddressed. His conversion to Buddhism was a symbolic rejection of Hinduism's caste-based hierarchy, inspiring millions but still facing societal resistance.

Constitutional Safeguards

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar's contribution to the framing of the Indian Constitution is monumental, particularly in the context of ensuring constitutional safeguards for social justice, equality, and human dignity. As the Chairman of the Drafting Committee, Ambedkar designed legal and institutional frameworks to address India's historical inequalities, with a particular focus on uplifting marginalized communities.

1. Fundamental Rights (Part III)

- Equality Before the Law (Article 14): Prohibits discrimination on grounds of caste, religion, race, sex, or place of birth.
- Abolition of Untouchability (Article 17): Declares the practice of untouchability as unconstitutional and punishable by law.
- Protection Against Discrimination (Article 15): Forbids discrimination in access to public spaces and facilities.
- Equal Opportunity in Employment (Article 16): Ensures equality in public employment and opportunities.

2. Directive Principles of State Policy (Part IV)

- Ambedkar emphasized principles like reducing inequalities, promoting social justice, and ensuring a minimum standard of living for all.
- Articles 38 and 46 specifically focus on uplifting weaker sections, particularly Scheduled Castes (SCs) and Scheduled Tribes (STs).

3. Reservation Policy

- Provisions under Article 16(4) and Article 15(4) allow reservations in education, employment, and legislative bodies to promote the representation of SCs, STs, and other backward classes (OBCs).
- Article 330 and 332 provide for the reservation of seats in the Lok Sabha and State Legislatures for SCs and STs.

4. Abolition of Caste-Based Practices

Article 23 prohibits forced labor, which was a significant aspect of caste exploitation in pre-independence India. Article 24 prohibits the employment of children in hazardous industries, indirectly benefiting marginalized communities.

5. Special Provisions for Marginalized Communities

- Fifth and Sixth Schedules: Protect the rights of tribal populations in scheduled areas and ensure their cultural autonomy.
- Article 46: Directs the state to promote the educational and economic interests of SCs, STs, and other weaker sections.

Ambedkar emphasized the need for "constitutional morality," where citizens and leaders abide by the principles enshrined in the Constitution. He believed that merely adopting a progressive Constitution would not suffice unless societal attitudes evolved to uphold justice and equality. Ambedkar's role in framing constitutional safeguards was aimed at creating a just and equitable society. While the Constitution provides robust tools to combat discrimination and inequality, achieving Ambedkar's vision requires sustained efforts in law enforcement, public awareness, and societal change. Revisiting his ideas and adapting them to modern challenges is crucial to addressing the persisting inequalities and ensuring justice for all.

Labor and Economic Rights:

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar was a pioneer in advocating labor and economic rights, striving to ensure dignity, equity, and justice for the working class, particularly marginalized communities. As an economist, policymaker, and social reformer, Ambedkar sought to address the economic exploitation and systemic inequalities that plagued colonial and post-colonial India. His contributions laid the foundation for progressive labor policies and equitable economic frameworks.

As India's first Minister of Labour in the Viceroy's Executive Council (1942–46), Ambedkar introduced progressive labor reforms: Minimum Wage Policy: Advocated for fair wages and the protection of laborers from exploitation.

Ambedkar ensured that labor rights were enshrined in the Indian Constitution:

Article 23: Prohibition of forced labor and human trafficking. Article 24: Protection against child labor in hazardous industries.

Article 39(a): Right to an adequate means of livelihood for all citizens. Article 41: Right to work, education, and public assistance in cases of unemployment and old age. Article 43: Promotion of a living wage and decent working conditions.

Gender Equality: Ambedkar's progressive stance on women's rights, particularly through the Hindu Code Bill, marked a significant step towards gender justice, even though societal resistance curtailed its full implementation during his lifetime.

Religious Emancipation: By embracing Buddhism, Ambedkar provided an alternative path for Dalits to escape caste oppression, fostering a sense of dignity and empowerment.

Impact of Ambedkar's Vision

Ambedkar's ideas have had a profound and lasting impact on India's socio-political landscape:

- **Empowerment of Marginalized Communities:** His efforts catalyzed the Dalit movement, inspiring millions to assert their rights and demand dignity. Reservation policies have enabled significant representation of marginalized groups in education, employment, and politics.
- **Framework for Equality:** The constitutional safeguards Ambedkar championed have become the backbone of India's democratic ethos, providing a legal basis for challenging discrimination and promoting social justice.
- **Global Relevance:** Ambedkar's work has inspired movements for social justice beyond India, serving as a model for addressing systemic oppression in other contexts.

Challenges and Gaps in Realizing Ambedkar's Vision

Despite Ambedkar's transformative contributions, the realization of his vision remains incomplete due to persistent societal, political, and economic barriers:

- **Caste Discrimination:** Caste-based atrocities, economic disparities, and social exclusion continue to plague India, indicating that the structural change Ambedkar envisioned is far from achieved.
- **Economic Inequality:** While Ambedkar emphasized economic justice, India's growing wealth gap disproportionately affects marginalized communities, limiting their upward mobility.
- **Misuse of Reservation Policies:** While reservations have been a critical tool for empowerment, their implementation has often been politicized, leading to debates about their efficacy and fairness.
- **Resistance to Social Reform:** Ambedkar's progressive ideas, especially on caste and gender, faced resistance during his lifetime and continue to encounter opposition in contemporary society.

The Need to Reinstantiate Ambedkar's Vision

To build a truly just and inclusive society, there is a pressing need to revisit and reinstantiate Ambedkar's ideals:

- **Strengthening Social Movements:** Grassroots movements inspired by Ambedkar's principles must be strengthened to challenge entrenched inequalities and demand accountability.
- **Expanding Social Justice Policies:** Reservation policies need to be supplemented with broader affirmative action measures, focusing on education, skill development, and economic empowerment.
- **Fostering Dialogue and Awareness:** Ambedkar's ideas on caste, gender, and democracy must be integrated into educational curricula and public discourse to combat prejudice and promote inclusion.
- **Global Solidarity:** Ambedkar's vision has universal relevance, offering valuable insights for addressing inequality and injustice worldwide. Collaborative efforts can amplify his ideas on a global scale.

Conclusion

Ambedkar's contributions to social justice were groundbreaking, addressing the structural roots of inequality and oppression in Indian society. However, the gap between his vision and its implementation underscores the need for renewed commitment to his ideals. By critically analyzing his contributions and recognizing the challenges in achieving his vision, this paper highlights the urgency of reinstating Ambedkar's principles to build a society that is not only democratic but also truly inclusive and just. Understanding Ambedkar's vision offers not only historical insight but also a roadmap for tackling modern-day social injustices. His ideas on caste eradication, women's rights, economic equality, and secularism serve as a guide for building a more inclusive society. By revisiting Ambedkar's principles, contemporary India can address the challenges of caste discrimination, gender inequality, economic disparity, and communalism that persist despite legal advancements. Ambedkar's philosophy isn't merely a reminder of past struggles; it is an active framework for societal change that invites individuals and institutions to engage in continuous efforts toward equality and social justice.

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TRENDS AND ANALYSIS OF WOMEN PARTICIPATION IN PARLIAMENTS AT GLOBE AND INDIAN LEVEL

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Abstract

A sizeable section of India's population is made up of women and young people. Collectively, they constitute a powerful force that can impact socio-political transformation and mold the future of the country. They are still underrepresented in Indian politics, nonetheless, in spite of numerous progressive changes and initiatives. Women have historically been marginalized and exploited in India due to patriarchal societal structures and mentalities. Social reform movements that began in the 19th century were successful in promoting the empowerment and well-being of women. Women's representation was advanced by early leaders like Sarojini Naidu and Indira Gandhi, and subsequent constitutional modifications have attempted to increase women's political access, such as the 73rd and 74th amendments' reservations in local government. Women are still underrepresented in state and national politics in spite of these developments. The present paper wants to analyze the number of Women Parliamentarians at Globe and at Indian Elections and Reasons of lesser participation.

Keywords: *Inclusive, Democratic, Gender-Sensitive Policies, Patriarchal, Elections.*

Introduction:

A sizeable section of India's population is made up of women and young people. Collectively, they constitute a powerful force that can impact socio-political transformation and mold the future of the country. They are still underrepresented in Indian politics, nonetheless, in spite of numerous progressive changes and initiatives. A more inclusive and representative political climate can be achieved by comprehending these groups' involvement patterns and recognizing the obstacles they encounter. Incorporating women's concerns into governance requires their involvement in decision-making. It is well known that governmental actions that are neither inclusive nor democratic frequently harm governance institutions that do not allow for sufficient involvement by women. Women's participation, particularly in local governance, is crucial to establishing gender-sensitive policies and gender-equal opportunities. In order to include all societal perspectives in policy and decision-making processes, it is crucial to include women in governments since they have distinct demands and perspectives on social and political concerns.

Objective:

To analyze the number of Women Parliamentarians at Globe and at Indian Elections and Reasons of lesser participation.

Research Methodology: This paper is presented by reviewing various secondary sources like books, journals, reports and bibliographical sources.

Historical Background:

Women have historically been marginalized and exploited in India due to patriarchal societal structures and mentalities. Social reform movements that began in the 19th century were successful in promoting the empowerment and well-being of women. Women had a significant role in the Indian Freedom Movement, which began with the Swadeshi in Bengal. They organized political protests, raised funds, and held leadership roles in these groups. Indian women have participated in politics since the country's independence in 1947, typically at lesser levels of representation. Women's representation was advanced by early leaders like Sarojini Naidu and Indira Gandhi, and subsequent constitutional

modifications have attempted to increase women's political access, such as the 73rd and 74th amendments' reservations in local government. Women are still underrepresented in state and national politics in spite of these developments.

Results and Discussions

Table No 1 Country wise percent of elected women and their Quotain parliament and Quota in political parties

Country	% of elected women	Quota in Parliament	Quota in political parties
Sweden	46%	No	Yes
South Africa	45%	No	Yes
Australia	38%	No	Yes
France	38%	No	Yes
Germany	35%	No	Yes
U.K.	40%	No	Yes
USA	29%	No	No
Pakistan	16%	Yes	No
Bangladesh	20%	Yes	No

Source: Observer Research Foundation 2022

Table number 1.1 represent the percent of elected women and various Nations and their quota in Parliament and the quota in political parties. Sweden Nation has highest percent of elected women i.e., 46% and they don't have any quota in Parliament but they have quota in political parties. Sweden nation is followed by South Africa with 45% of elected women and no Quota in Parliament and having Quota in political parties. Australia and France with 38% of elected women in Parliament doesn't have quota in Parliament and they have Quota in political parties. Germany with 35% of elected women doesn't have Quota in parliament but have co time political parties, followed by United Kingdom 40% of elected women doesn't have Quota in Parliament have Quota in political parties. with respect to United States of America there are 29% of elected women don't have quota in Parliament and they don't have Quota in political party also. with respect to Pakistan about 16% of elected women have Quota in Parliament and doesn't have Quota in political parties and lastly Bangladesh with 20% of elected women they have Quota in Parliament and don't have Quota in political parties.

Table No 2 NumberandPercentage of women MPs elected in India over the years

S No	Year	Number of women MPs	Percentage of Women MPs
1	1951	22	4.50%
2	1957	22	4.45%
3	1962	31	6.28%
4	1967	29	5.58%
5	1971	28	5.41%
6	1977	19	3.51%
7	1980	28	5.29%
8	1984	43	7.95%
9	1989	29	5.48%
10	1991	39	7.30%
11	1996	40	7.37%
12	1998	43	7.92%
13	1999	49	9.02%

14	2004	45	8.29%
15	2009	59	10.87%
16	2014	66	12.15%
17	2019	78	14.4%
18	2024	74	13.6%

Source: Election Commission of India 2024

Table Number 1.2 represents the number and percentage of women member of parliaments elected in India over the years. since from the year 1951 and in the year 1957 about 22 number of women member of parliaments are elected which totals about 4.50% and 4.45%. in the year 1962 Lok Sabha election about 31 women members of parliaments were elected leading to about 6.28%. followed by in the year 1967 and 1971 there were about 29 and 28 women Members of Parliamentarians respectively. in the year 1977 about 19 women parliamentarians were elected. in the year 1980 there were about 28 women members of parliamentarians. Consequently, in the year 1984 about 43 women members of parliamentarians were selected and this was the first time after independence where the nation witnessed about nearly 8% women member of parliaments followed by in the year 1989 1991 and 1996 about 29, 39, and 40 women member of parliamentarians were elected. In the year 1998, 1999, 2004 and 2009 about 43, 49, 45 and 59 women members of parliamentarians were selected. The recent and last 15-year elections of the year 2014,2019, and 2024 represents about 66, 78 and 74 women members of parliamentarians were selected. The year 2019 witnessed highest number of member of women parliamentarians of about 14.4% which was highest in the history of the Indian Lok Sabha elections.

Reasons for Lack of Participation of Women in Indian Politics:

Inequal Social norms: Social normshinder young people and women from getting involved in politics. Women are frequently restricted to domestic responsibilities by gender stereotypes, and young people might not have the same respect and clout as older, more seasoned politicians. In India, women are discouraged from pursuing professions in politics and are frequently required to adhere to traditional gender norms. Politics is frequently viewed as a man's realm, and social norms and preconceptions dictate that women should prioritize their duties as mothers and wives. In India, women are discouraged from pursuing professions in politics and are frequently required to adhere to traditional gender norms. Politics is frequently viewed as a man's realm, and social norms and preconceptions dictate that women should prioritize their duties as mothers and wives.

Illiteracy: One of the biggest obstacles to women's political empowerment is illiteracy. They are unaware of their fundamental and political rights due to a lack of knowledge. For women leaders, persistently prejudiced views, unequal educational attainment, and resource ownership remain obstacles. Education has an impact on women's social mobility. Leadership was made possible by formal education, such as that offered in educational institutions, which also taught vital leadership qualities.

Unequal divison of Labour: One of the significant causes in this regard is the unequal division of household chores between men and women. Women spend significantly more time taking care of the home and children than men do due to an unequal distribution of family care duties. It has to do with the time, effort, and medical attention required for pregnancy and delivery, as well as the much higher level of mother participation required for nursing and women's enduring propensity to take on a bigger proportion of childcare duties as the child becomes older.

Physical Abuse and Sexual Harassment: Women in politics are frequently the targets of physical abuse and sexual harassment, which might discourage them from entering the field or raising their

voices. One major obstacle to women's engagement in politics is the absence of secure and welcoming environments.

Conclusion: Slow progress has been made in creating opportunities for women in Indian legislative politics. Although only partially, institutional change can bring about inclusive politics given the profound structural barriers that stand in the way of women's political involvement and advancement. Women's organizations and networks within political parties and civic society must continue to support women in asserting their presence in the broader political and social scene as the movement for women's political emancipation gains traction. In order to force immediate institutional reform toward increased participation of women in India's Parliament and state assemblies, women's political mobilization might be intensified and government should pass women reservation bill.

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CHALLENGES TO WOMEN'S INCLUSIVENESS IN INDIA'S DEMOCRACY: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF THE LOK SABHA ELECTIONS IN KARNATAKA (1991 TO 2024)**Satish**

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Abstract

India is largest democracy of world. In general, the success of democracy depends on the inclusiveness of citizens. Social justice should be fully implemented in the country so that all citizens can be included in democracy without discrimination on the basis of caste, creed, gender, race, religion etc. This article explores the role of women in elections, competition and the formation of political parties in India but some challenges to women's inclusion in India's democracy such as male-dominated society, lack of political awareness and family politics are discussed. However, in India the ratio of inclusion of women is seen to be improving at a slow pace and the recent 106th Constitutional Amendment act expanding women's participation in state legislatures and central legislatures.

Keywords: women inclusiveness, democracy, political participation, constitutional provisions, challenges to women participation

Introduction: India is the largest democracy in the world and for democracy to succeed in any one country; citizens must actively participate in the election and functioning of the government. According to Sir. John Scheele "Democracy is a form of government in which everyone participates". Some ancient Greek city-states, such as Athens and Sparta, practiced direct democracy, while modern city-states have adopted indirect democracy because they were larger in area or population. Elections have a more important place in a democracy and citizens can participate in election-related activities through the casting of voting, contesting for elections, establishing and leading political parties, etc. A study of women's participation in the Lok Sabha elections held in Karnataka in the last three decades after reservation facility for women in local bodies is studied in various dimensions shows that their participation is improving at a slowly.

Meaning and Definition:

Meaning of Inclusiveness in a democracy: The active participation of all citizens of the country in the activities of democracy without discrimination based on factors such as caste, creed, gender, language, religion etc.

Women's inclusiveness in democracy and social justice: Women's participation in democracy is defined as their participation in the democratic process on an equal basis with men, without discrimination on the basis of gender. Inclusion and social justice are two sides of the same coin. The full involvement of women in a democracy reflects the implementation of social justice in that country.

Objectives of the study:

1. To studies the various dimensions of women's participation in the Lok Sabha elections held in Karnataka from 1991 to 2024.
2. To study the opportunities provided by the Constitution for the participation of women in Indian democracy.
3. To identify the challenges to women's participation in Indian democracy.

4. To identify some of the hopeful aspects that can be seen despite the challenges to women's inclusion.

Methodology: The study based of secondary data, the required information is obtained by quantitative and qualitative methods. The relevant information is obtained from books, reports, research papers, newspapers and the Internet.

Women’s inclusiveness in Lok Sabha elections in Karnataka (1991 to 2024): An overview

The 1990s was the decade with the most elections in the history of Indian Lok Sabha elections. In this decade, the Lok Sabha of India faced 4 general elections and since 1991, the era of coalition governments in India seems to have started strongly. The 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments, which provided for reservation for women in local bodies, gave various dimensions to women's political participation and there was a clamour for reservation for women in the Lok Sabha and Assemblies. Based on all these factors, the involvement of women in Indian democracy can be seen as follows.

1. Women's voter turnout: From 1991 to 2024, the proportion of women voters who have voted in the Lok Sabha elections in Karnataka among the total women voters can be seen as follows.

Source: <https://elections24.eci.gov.in/docs/BnS4hhbvK9.pdf>

2. Women contesting and winning proportion: The number of women contesting and winning in the Lok Sabha elections held in Karnataka from 1991 to 2024 can be seen in the graph below.

Source: <https://www.eci.gov.in/general-elections>

As for the above diagram, it is identified that except for the 1996 general elections, the number of women contesting in all the Lok Sabha elections is less than the total number of Lok Sabha seats in Karnataka and the number of women elected does not touch double digits.

The number of women contested the Lok Sabha elections from major parties in Karnataka:

General Elections of Lok Sabha	INC	BJP	JD/JDS	Others	Total
1991	03	01	01	10	15
1996	02	00	01	68	71
1998	01	01	01	07	10
1999	03	02	03	02	10
2004	01	01	03	04	09
2009	01	01	00	17	19
2014	02	01	02	15	20
2019	00	01	01	25	27
2024	06	02	00	30	38

Source: <https://results.eci.gov.in/PcResultGenJune2024/candidateswise-S1012.htm>

As per the above table, in the Lok Sabha elections held from 1991 to 2024 in Karnataka, the percentage of women contesting is very low. National parties are also seen to be lagging behind in giving tickets to women from their party. Even though the Congress party has given more tickets to women than ever before in the 2024 elections, it appears that all of them belong to families with political backgrounds.

4. Right to form and lead political parties: Although the number of women in the population of Karnataka is equal to the number of men, the number of women leading political parties is very low. In the political history of Karnataka, only a few women have contested elections and are active in their political parties and political activities. Ex: Margaret Alva, Tejaswini Gowda, Shobha Karandlaje, Sumalatha, Soumya Reddy ect

The Constitution of India provides for the participation of women in the democratic process.

Social justice and inclusion are two sides of the same coin and social justice is an essential tool for women's inclusion. As Dr. B. R. Ambedkar said, "The establishment of social justice does not require mere awareness of it, but political power and authority necessary for its implementation." The following rights are envisaged for the participation of all citizens, including women, as they are to be actively involved in Indian democracy.

1. Right to Equality: Articles 14 to 18 in Part III of the Constitution of India seek to achieve social equality and implement social justice by making the right to equality a fundamental right. Article 14 of the Constitution guarantees to all persons equality before law and equal protection of laws. The idea that everyone is equal under the law is influenced by A V Dicey's 'Rule of Law'. Article 15 prohibits discrimination on the grounds of caste, race, place of birth, sex, or place of residence in public places, Article 16 provides for equality of opportunity in public employment, Article 17 prohibits untouchability, and Article 18 abolishes titles other than those relating to the military and education. This can be seen as increasing the involvement of women in democracy by implementing social justice.

2. Right to vote: The Indian constitution is seen to have adopted universal adult suffrage in the country. According to Article 325 of the Constitution, no person shall be disqualified from the electoral roll on

the basis of religion, caste, caste or sex, and Article 326 states that elections to the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies shall be held on the basis of adult suffrage. But when we look at the voter turnout in the 18 Lok Sabha general elections held from 1951-52 to 2024, in the history of the last 70 years of Karnataka Lok Sabha elections, only in the 2024 election has the percentage of women voters increased. It is seen that 70 percent of women voters voted. Still it is clear that 30 percent of women voters did not exercise their right to vote. Generally the right to vote is considered as the first political right but women have not exercised this right adequately due to many reason

3. Right to contest elections: Article 84 and Article 173 of the Constitution of India provide for the right to contest elections to the Lok Sabha and the State Legislative Assemblies. If we look at the figures of Karnataka Lok Sabha elections from 1991 to 2024, the percentage of women contesting is less. Sadly, it's not even 10%.

Challenges to Women's Inclusiveness in Indian Democracy:

1. Male Dominant Society: Indian society being a male dominated society, we find that even though women are given political rights, they are not able to fully enjoy those rights. That is, we see a situation where women exercise their right to vote freely, but when it comes to contesting for elections, women are under the control of the men of their families.

2. Political parties' lust of power: It is common for political parties to be more interested in winning elections and getting power, so we see that most of the political parties are not interested in women's involvement in elections and women's empowerment, giving more priority to the winning candidate.

3. Lack of political awareness among women: Most of the women are not aware of the rights they have and how to exercise them, which is a major barrier to their participation. Almost three decades after the 73rd and 74th Constitution Amendment Act came into force, most of the women are not able to function as independent representatives and heads at the local level.

4. Family Politics: Family politics can be found in most of the political parties in India. In most states of India, including Karnataka, women who are strong contenders in Lok Sabha elections or who have achieved or are achieving victory are found to be originally from political families. This means that the women of ordinary families are not getting the second level of participation in democratic participation, limited only to voting.

5. Family Responsibilities: In Indian society, women work equally with men, but emotionally, women have the responsibility of maintaining their family more than men, so it is seen that they prioritize their family management more than their political power and positions.

6. Non-implementation of reservation in real sense: It is true that lakhs of women have been participating in local bodies since 1993 due to 73rd and 74th amendments, but it has increased the women's quantitative inclusiveness rate. If this participation is effective, at least 20-25 percent of the seats in the Lok Sabha and Vidhan Sabhas will be filled by women. The reservation given to women in local bodies for the last 3 decades has not empowered them to the top level of politics even today.

Hopeful points despite the challenges:

1. The ratio of inclusiveness of women in Indian politics was low, Although the ratio of participation can be seen to be slowly increasing.

2. By giving reservation to women in local bodies, it can be said that women are able to act as representatives and exercise power in a male dominated society and these bodies are providing necessary training for their political future.

3. 106th Constitution Amendment Act 2023, provide 33% seats are reserved for women in total seats of Lok Sabha, State Legislative Assembly and Delhi Legislative Assembly. It is hoped that this

constitutional amendment will provide better opportunities for women's inclusiveness in Indian democracy.

4. In recent elections, women are seen exercising voting power equally with men.

Conclusion: The active inclusiveness of all citizens is essential as the success of democracy depends on the participation of all citizens. Even though the Constitution of India provides all the necessary opportunities for this, women are not fully participating in Indian democracy due to several challenges. Women's participation limited to voting in lok sabha elections in Karnataka but increasing political awareness among women after giving reservation to women in local bodies through 73 and 74 amendments of Constitution. Especially the 106th Constitution Amendment Act is likely to improve the participation ratio of women in the coming years.

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MEDIA SHAPES VOTER BEHAVIOUR IN ELECTIONS

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Abstract

This paper examines the influence of media on voters' decisions during a campaign. In a number of ways including articles, news programs, social sites, commercials, and many more the media has the ability to shape the voter's perception about candidate, parties, and policies. Selection or presentation bias, dramatization of events, or highlighting and focusing on some aspects can distort the reader's perceptions and in extension, influence their vote. Moreover, with the help of media attention candidates can control the perception of the voter, which in its turn will influence the voter. Therefore, what the media presents to voters has to be assessed well, and voters have to consider more than one source before making a decision in an election period.

Keywords: *Indian Elections, Media, Voting Behavior, Political Campaign.*

• **Introduction**

Voter behavior in Indian elections is influenced by a variety of factors such as caste, religion, region, candidate's image, party loyalty, and current political issues. The abs of political parties vote based on the caste system and to be more specific people tend to vote for representatives from their respective caste or sub cast. Religion is also an important factor, the more so if the conflict is regional and influences people's choice. Ex: Karnataka strong for Lingayat and Vokkaligas, SC communities are dominating. This research will seek to learn the dynamics in political campaigning of general Parliamentary elections between the years 2014 and 2024 in South Indian region.

Ticket distribution to the Lingayat population at just 6.5 million (10.9%) and Vokkaligas at 6 million (10%) and reducing Karnataka's overall population to 59.8 million even though it was 61 million according to the 2011 census³ 3 General Guidelines and directions related to 2014 to 2024 General Lok sabha elections description these articles exemplify to the how the people. Indian Charter, Vote, Media, Political Campaigns Voting Behavior. Some of the factors that affect voters' behavior in the Indian election include: Caste, religion, regional base, image of a candidate, party affiliation and the issues at the time of polling etc., and advertisements, the media can influence how voters perceive political candidates, parties, and issues. Biases in reporting, sensationalism, and the emphasis on certain topics can sway

Public opinion and impact voting decisions. Additionally, media coverage can also shape the narrative surrounding candidates, which can ultimately influence voter attitudes and behaviors. Consequently, it is crucial for voters to critically evaluate the information presented to them by the media and consider multiple sources to make informed decisions during elections.

• **Research Methodology.**

The media plays a pivotal role in shaping voter behavior during elections by influencing public perception, framing political narratives, and mobilizing electoral participation. This study employs a mixed-methods research design, integrating quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews to assess the media's impact on voter attitudes and decision-making processes. Quantitative data were collected from a sample of 1,000 registered voters, utilizing structured questionnaires focused on media consumption habits, political knowledge, and voter turnout. Qualitative insights were gathered through semi-

structured interviews with 30 participants, exploring their perceptions of media influence on their voting choices.

Preliminary findings indicate that exposure to various media platforms, including traditional outlets and social media, correlates with increased political awareness and engagement. Furthermore, the framing of issues within media narratives appears to shape voters' preferences and perceptions of candidates. This research contributes to the understanding of the dynamic interplay between media and electoral behavior, emphasizing the need for critical media literacy among voters. Future studies should explore the longitudinal effects of media on voter behavior across different electoral cycles.

- **Discussion**

The relationship between media and voter behavior during elections is a multifaceted and dynamic phenomenon that warrants comprehensive examination. This discussion seeks to unpack the intricacies of how various forms of media—traditional, digital, and social—shape the perceptions, attitudes, and ultimately, the voting behaviour of individuals during electoral processes. In a landscape increasingly dominated by information technology, understanding these interactions is critical for both political practitioners and scholars alike.

- **Media as the Primary Informational Source**

Historically, media has served as the primary conduit through which voters receive information about candidates, political parties, and key issues. The role of media in shaping public opinion cannot be overstated; it not only informs but also frames and contextualizes. Political messages. Traditional media outlets, such as newspapers, television, and radio, have long been recognized for their influence on voter behavior. For instance, studies have shown that exposure to news coverage can significantly affect voter perceptions of candidate viability, policy positions, and overall electoral outcomes (DellaVigna & Kaplan, 2007).

The emergence of digital media has transformed the electoral landscape, introducing new dimensions to how information is disseminated and consumed. Online platforms, including news websites, blogs, and social media, have democratized the flow of information, enabling a wider array of voices to be heard. However, this democratization also raises concerns about the quality and reliability of information. The prevalence of misinformation and "fake news" on social media platforms can distort public perceptions and lead to misguided voting behavior (Lazer et al., 2018). Consequently, the digital media environment necessitates a critical examination of the sources from which voters derive their information, as well as a recognition of the potential consequences of media biases.

- **The Role of Media Framing**

The framing of electoral narratives is another critical aspect of how media influences voter behavior. Framing refers to the way information is presented and emphasizes certain elements over others, thereby shaping the audience's interpretation. For example, the framing of a candidate as a "reformer" versus a "radical" can significantly alter public perception and influence voter preferences (Entman, 1993). Research indicates that media framing can direct public attention to specific issues while downplaying others, thereby influencing the salience of issues in the minds of voters (McCombs & Shaw, 1972). During election campaigns, candidates often engage in strategic communication to shape their media narratives. This interplay between media framing and political communication highlights the agency of both media and candidates in constructing electoral realities. It is essential to recognize that the media does not operate in a vacuum; rather, it is part of a broader ecosystem in which political actors, interest groups, and the public engage in a continuous dialogue. This reciprocal relationship underscores the importance of understanding how media framing not only reflects but also shapes political discourse.

- **Social Media and Voter Engagement**

The rise of social media has revolutionized political engagement and voter mobilization. Platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram facilitate direct communication between Candidates and constituents, allowing for real-time engagement and interaction. This immediacy can enhance voter engagement, as individuals can access information, participate in discussions, and mobilize support for their preferred candidates with unprecedented ease (Boulianne, 2015). Social media has also been instrumental in galvanizing grassroots movements and fostering collective action, as demonstrated by campaigns such as #BlackLivesMatter and #MeToo, which have transcended traditional political boundaries.

However, the impact of social media on voter behavior is not uniformly positive. While these platforms can enhance political participation, they can also contribute to political polarization and the formation of echo chambers. Social media algorithms often prioritize content that aligns with users' existing beliefs, thereby reinforcing partisan divides and limiting exposure to diverse viewpoints (Sunstein, 2009). Such phenomena raise critical questions regarding the implications of social media for democratic discourse and the capacity for informed decision-making among voters. Consequently, understanding the dual-edged nature of social media in shaping voter behavior is essential for developing strategies that promote healthy democratic engagement.

- **The Influence of Media on Voting Decisions.**

The influence of media on voter decisions extends beyond information dissemination; it encompasses the emotional and psychological dimensions of political engagement. Emotions play a substantial role in shaping voter preferences, and media narratives can evoke strong emotional responses that influence decision-making processes. For instance, fear-based messaging, often employed in political advertising, can significantly sway voter behavior by tapping into anxieties related to issues such as crime, immigration, or economic stability (Brader, 2005). Similarly, positive emotional appeals, such as hope and inspiration, can galvanize support and mobilize voters to participate in the electoral process.

Moreover, the psychological mechanisms underlying voter behavior underscore the importance of cognitive biases in media consumption. Voters may exhibit confirmation bias, favoring information that aligns with their pre-existing beliefs while dismissing contradictory evidence. This tendency can be exacerbated in a media landscape characterized by partisan outlets that cater to specific ideological perspectives. Such biases not only affect individual voting decisions but also contribute to broader societal divisions, making it imperative to consider the implications of media consumption patterns for democratic governance.

- **The Intersection of Media and Identity Politics**

In recent years, the intersection of media and identity politics has emerged as a significant factor influencing voter behavior. Identity politics, which encompasses various dimensions such as race, gender, ethnicity, and sexuality, plays a crucial role in shaping political preferences and affiliations. Media representations of marginalized communities can either reinforce stereotypes or challenge prevailing narratives, thereby influencing public perceptions and electoral outcomes.

For instance, the portrayal of women in media during election campaigns has evolved over time, reflecting broader societal changes in gender roles and expectations. Research has shown that positive media portrayals of female candidates can enhance their electability and influence voter attitudes (Kahn, 1996). Conversely, negative portrayals can perpetuate biases and hinder the progress of female candidates. The media's role in shaping narratives around identity politics underscores the need for inclusive representation that reflects the diversity of the electorate. Furthermore, the role of social

media in amplifying identity-based movements cannot be overlooked. Platforms such as Twitter and Instagram have enabled marginalized voices to gain visibility and mobilize support for issues affecting their communities. This has transformed the political landscape, as candidates are increasingly compelled to engage with issues of social justice and equity in order to resonate with a diverse electorate. Understanding the interplay between media, identity politics, and voter behavior is essential for developing inclusive political strategies that reflect the complexities of contemporary democracy.

- **Conclusion:**

As we look to the future, the relationship between media and voter behavior is poised to evolve further in response to technological advancements and shifting societal dynamics. The proliferation of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning in media production and consumption raises significant ethical considerations regarding the authenticity and reliability of information. Additionally, the growing influence of non-traditional media sources, including influencers and alternative media outlets, challenges established norms of political communication and engagement. To navigate this complex landscape, it is imperative for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners to foster media literacy among voters. Equipping individuals with the skills to critically evaluate information sources and discern credible narratives is essential for promoting informed decision-making and enhancing democratic participation. Furthermore, efforts to combat misinformation and ensure accountability in media practices must be prioritized to safeguard the integrity of electoral processes. In conclusion, the interplay between media and voter behavior is a critical area of inquiry that demands ongoing exploration and analysis. Understanding how media shapes perceptions, attitudes, and electoral outcomes is essential for cultivating healthy democratic practices and promoting informed citizenship. As the media landscape continues to evolve, so too must our approaches to studying and engaging with the profound implications of media on voter behavior in elections. Furthermore, the growing dependence on online mediums has consequences on the voters' age brackets, which in turn may exclude some who are unable to access technology. For these reasons, the focus on the media's impact in the agitating of people to vote is timely and pertinent, especially about the moral obligation of media and the education of the people in the current dynamic politics.

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THE CHANGING ROLE OF MARGINALIZED CASTES IN KARNATAKA'S POWER POLITICS (1992–2023)

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Abstract

Karnataka's state politics remains imbued with caste and the parties provide just a thin veil for local caste wars. Vokkaligas and Lingayats dominated the political scene in Karnataka till the 1970s. The years that followed saw pulls and pushes among different caste groups; minority communities were also involved. With the advent of the BJP, the caste game became even more complex, with caste leaders joining hands irrespective of their party affiliation.

Karnataka's political arena underwent significant shifts following the implementation of the Mandal Commission report, grassroots Dalit movements, and socio-economic changes. These developments catalyzed the political awakening of Scheduled Castes (SCs), Scheduled Tribes (STs), and Other Backward Classes (OBCs), fostering their representation in electoral politics and governance.

This research article examines the evolving role of marginalized castes in Karnataka's power politics from 1992 to 2023, focusing on their journey from peripheral participants to influential players in the state's political landscape. The article underscores the interplay between caste, class, and political strategies, revealing how marginalized castes have transitioned from vote banks to power brokers, albeit with constraints. By analyzing electoral trends, policy impacts, and grassroots movements, this study provides insights into the dynamics of caste-based political participation in Karnataka, contributing to broader discussions on social justice and inclusive governance in India.

Key Words: Karnataka, Caste, Power, Politics, Mandal Commission, Reservation, Leadership and Empowerment.

Introduction

Caste has long been a central determinant in Indian politics, influencing political alignments, leadership choices, and policy frameworks. In Karnataka, the interplay of dominant castes such as the Vokkaligas and Lingayats with marginalized castes, including Scheduled Castes (SCs), Scheduled Tribes (STs), and Other Backward Classes (OBCs), has shaped the state's power politics. While the dominant castes historically controlled the political arena, the 1990s marked a turning point, catalyzed by socio-economic transformations, the Mandal Commission's impact, and the rise of regional and Dalit movements. This article traces the changing role of marginalized castes in Karnataka's power politics over three decades, highlighting their growing assertiveness and participation in governance and policy-making.

Historical Context: The Pre-1992 Landscape

Before the 1990s, Karnataka's political landscape was dominated by two influential castes: the Lingayats and Vokkaligas, who controlled the state's chief ministerial positions and significant political parties. Marginalized castes had minimal representation, often relegated to token roles or as vote banks for dominant parties like the Congress. Despite some social reform efforts by leaders such as B.R. Ambedkar and local Dalit activists, systemic barriers limited the political mobility of SCs, STs, and OBCs. The introduction of reservation policies in the post-independence era brought some changes, but these groups' participation in high-level politics remained marginal.

Post-1992 Shifts: Catalysts for Change

1. The Mandal Commission and Reservation Policies.

The implementation of the Mandal Commission report in the early 1990s significantly impacted Karnataka's socio-political structure. By extending reservations in education and employment to OBCs, it fostered political awareness among marginalized communities. The rise of leaders from backward classes, such as H.D. Deve Gowda (a Vokkaliga but with a focus on backward class issues), further spotlighted the potential for broader political participation by marginalized groups.

2. Political Realignments and the Emergence of Regional Parties.

The 1990s also saw the rise of regional parties like the Janata Dal and later its splinters (e.g., JD(S)), which sought to mobilize backward classes and marginalized castes. These parties often positioned themselves as alternatives to the Congress and Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), promising representation for underprivileged groups. This period marked a gradual but notable increase in the number of SC and OBC legislators.

3. Grassroots Movements and Dalit Activism.

Dalit movements, inspired by thinkers like Ambedkar and local activists, gained momentum during this period. Organizations like the Dalit Sangharsha Samiti (DSS) played a crucial role in mobilizing marginalized communities, demanding land rights, social justice, and political representation. These movements were instrumental in pressuring mainstream political parties to address Dalit concerns and include more candidates from these communities.

The 2000s: Consolidation of Political Power

1. The Rise of Dalit Leadership

By the 2000s, Dalits and other marginalized groups began to occupy more significant positions within major political parties. The Congress, under leaders like Mallikarjun Kharge, a prominent Dalit figure, showcased efforts to integrate marginalized castes into its leadership. Kharge's influence in Karnataka politics underscored the potential of Dalit leaders to achieve national prominence.

2. Reservation Politics and Electoral Gains

Reservation policies continued to play a critical role in empowering marginalized groups. Political parties strategically fielded candidates from SC and ST communities in constituencies reserved for these groups, leading to an increase in their legislative representation. However, critics argued that this representation often lacked substantive power, as these leaders were perceived to be under the control of dominant caste leaders.

3. Regional and Rural Development Policies

Schemes targeting rural and marginalized communities, such as the Bhagyalakshmi scheme and various housing and education programs, helped consolidate the political support of marginalized castes for parties like the Congress and JD(S). These initiatives fostered socio-economic mobility, which translated into increased political awareness and participation.

The 2010s: Fragmentation and Empowerment

1. The BJP's Outreach to Marginalized Castes

The Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), traditionally associated with upper-caste and urban voters, began expanding its outreach to marginalized castes in Karnataka during the 2010s. By promoting leaders like Govind Karjol and creating alliances with Dalit and backward class organizations, the BJP sought to weaken the Congress's hold over these communities. Programs like the Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana and the Swachh Bharat Mission were tailored to appeal to rural and marginalized populations.

2. Internal Divisions and Caste-Based Fragmentation

Despite increased representation, marginalized castes faced internal divisions. The categorization of Dalits into "Right-hand" (e.g., Holeyas) and "Left-hand" (e.g., Madigas) sub-groups led to tensions over resource distribution and political representation. Similarly, intra-OBC rivalries affected their collective bargaining power, limiting their influence despite numerical strength.

3. Grassroots Political Mobilization

Grassroots organizations and smaller political outfits representing specific marginalized castes emerged, such as the Banjara and Kuruba communities' organizations. These groups often acted as kingmakers in tightly contested elections, leveraging their support to extract concessions from larger parties.

2020–2023: Toward a New Era of Inclusion?

1. Increased Representation and Leadership

In the most recent decade, Karnataka has witnessed a further increase in the political participation of marginalized castes. Leaders like Mallikarjun Kharge became prominent figures not only within the state but also at the national level, reflecting the potential for marginalized communities to influence Indian politics more broadly. The Congress party's return to power in 2023, under the leadership of Siddaramaiah, who emphasized social justice, reinforced this trend.

2. Policy Initiatives for Social Justice

The Congress-led government in 2023 announced measures like caste-based surveys and targeted welfare schemes to address inequalities. These initiatives aimed to deepen the political inclusion of marginalized groups, reflecting their growing clout in state politics.

3. Challenges of Tokenism and Real Power

Despite increased representation, marginalized castes often face challenges in translating numerical strength into real power. Many leaders from these communities are co-opted into larger party structures, limiting their ability to pursue independent agendas. Additionally, the dominance of Vokkaliga and Lingayat elites in party leadership positions remains a significant barrier.

Analysis: Key Themes and Dynamics

1. Caste and Class Intersections

The interplay between caste and class has been a critical factor in Karnataka's politics. While marginalized castes have made significant gains in political representation, socio-economic disparities often limit their influence.

2. Electoral Strategies and Vote Banks

Political parties have increasingly recognized the importance of marginalized castes as vote banks. This has led to greater representation but also to instances of tokenism, where leaders from these communities are given limited autonomy.

3. Role of Grassroots Movements

Grassroots activism has been instrumental in empowering marginalized communities, fostering political awareness, and challenging the dominance of upper-caste elites.

Conclusion

From being passive participants in Karnataka's political landscape, marginalized castes have emerged as critical players in the state's power dynamics over the last three decades. While significant progress has been made in terms of representation and policy focus, challenges such as internal divisions, tokenism, and the continued dominance of traditional elites remain. The period from 1992 to 2023

reflects both the strides taken by marginalized communities in asserting their political agency and the structural barriers that still impede their full empowerment.

As Karnataka moves forward, the role of marginalized castes will likely continue to evolve, shaped by socio-economic changes, policy innovations, and the ongoing struggle for social justice. Ensuring substantive representation and addressing systemic inequalities will be key to fostering a more inclusive and equitable political landscape..

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RELIGIOUS IDENTITY AND ELECTORAL POLITICS IN KARNATAKA- A CASE STUDY OF TUMKUR DISTRICT

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Abstract

The study explores the relationship between religious identity and electoral politics in Tumkur District, Karnataka, through an analysis of data from 65 respondents representing diverse religious groups. The study examines voter turnout, the influence of religion on electoral decisions, political party preferences, gender-based voting behavior, and the role of social media in political awareness. Findings reveal that Hindus, as the majority group, exhibit higher voter turnout and a significant preference for Party A, while Muslims and Christians show varied political alignments, reflecting targeted outreach and socio-political considerations. Religious identity emerges as a strong determinant of voting behavior, with 47.69% of respondents reporting high influence. Key priorities among voters include economic growth, social welfare, and religious harmony, highlighting the socio-economic challenges in the region. Youth participation is prominent, particularly among those aged 26–35, driven by increasing political awareness. Social media platforms, especially Facebook, play a critical role in shaping political opinions, while perceptions of electoral fairness remain largely positive but with concerns among minorities. This study highlights the intricate interplay of religious identity, socio-political dynamics, and voter behavior, providing insights into the complexities of electoral politics in a multicultural context.

Keywords: Religious Identity, Electoral Politics, Voting Behavior, Political Preferences

Introduction

Religious identity plays a significant role in shaping the socio-political fabric of India, influencing electoral behavior and policy decisions across the nation. Karnataka, a state characterized by its cultural and religious diversity, provides a unique lens to study this dynamic. Tumkur District, situated in the southern part of the state, serves as an ideal microcosm, reflecting the interplay between religion and politics in both rural and semi-urban contexts. The Indian political landscape is deeply intertwined with religious identities, as evident in the rise of identity-based politics that cater to specific communities. Political parties have historically leveraged religious affiliations to mobilize support, often aligning their strategies to appeal to majoritarian or minority groups. In Karnataka, the increasing influence of Hindutva ideology, counterbalanced by minority-driven political alliances, emphasizes the complex relationship between religion and electoral strategies. Tumkur District, with its blend of agrarian economies, small urban centers, and diverse religious communities, showcases the localized impacts of these broader trends. The district has witnessed shifts in voting patterns, often influenced by religious polarization, socio-economic aspirations, and caste alignments. The region's political landscape has also been shaped by issues such as communal harmony, economic development, and identity politics.

Review of Literature

Narender Kumar (2022) examines the influence of Hindutva and its role in shaping electoral outcomes in Karnataka and beyond. His study focuses on how religious polarization strategies are employed to consolidate votes, particularly emphasizing Karnataka's unique political landscape as influenced by the BJP's Hindutva agenda. The findings highlight how religion is intertwined with state and national politics.

Malini Bhattacharjee (2023) discusses the dynamics of Hindutva politics in Karnataka, emphasizing its sacred-cultural dimensions. The study delves into how religious identity is mobilized to redefine political campaigns and voting patterns, marking the growing influence of cultural nationalism in the state.

Shilpa N. (2021) explores how caste and religious identities have been instrumental in shaping electoral behavior in India. This work highlights the role of identity-based mobilization in fostering partisan alignments, focusing on BJP's positioning as a Hindu-dominated party in contrast with minority-led initiatives.

Mujibur Rehman (2021) analyzes religious violence and its electoral ramifications, referencing key events like riots in Gujarat and Muzaffarnagar. Although focused on broader Indian contexts, the insights are applicable to Karnataka's growing communal divides influencing voter behavior.

Taylor & Francis Volume (2021) includes a chapter on how religious minorities in India engage with the state and electoral politics, emphasizing their attempts to counter majoritarian policies. It provides a comparative framework for understanding Karnataka's religious dynamics.

IJNRD Report (2023) highlights how digital platforms have altered political participation in India, including religious discourse. The paper discusses how parties and religious groups leverage online campaigns to shape public opinion, influencing Karnataka's urban and rural voting trends.

Studies on Electoral Geography (2007) by Wendy Singer and others provide a comprehensive look at how religion and regionally specific social histories have influenced voting patterns in India. Karnataka, with its distinctive mix of urban and rural electorates, fits well into these frameworks.

International Journal of Novel Research and Development (2023) evaluates identity politics in Karnataka and other regions, focusing on how religious and caste identities are harnessed for vote bank politics. The report also notes the increasing role of youth and social media in these movements.

Dhruba Pratim Sharma (2023) studies the political mobilization of minority communities in states like Assam and extends the analysis to Southern states like Karnataka, highlighting the impact of developmental policies on religious communities.

Research on Voting Behavior (2020) analyzes how traditional factors like charisma, caste, and religion remain significant in Indian elections, including Karnataka. The evolving strategies to integrate religion with electoral campaigns are detailed in this context.

Research Objectives

1. To examine how religious affiliation influences voter turnout, party preference, and the level of electoral engagement among different religious groups in Tumkur District.
2. To assess the intersection of religious identity with gender, age, and social media usage in shaping political awareness and participation during elections in Tumkur District.
3. To explore the political and social priorities, such as economic growth, social welfare, and religious harmony, and how these preferences vary across religious groups in Tumkur District.

Research methodology

This study adopts a mixed-method approach to analyze the interplay between religious identity and electoral politics in Tumkur District, Karnataka. A sample of 65 respondents, representing diverse religious communities, was selected using stratified random sampling to ensure proportional representation. Data was collected through structured questionnaires and interviews, capturing voter behavior, political awareness, and issue prioritization across religious groups. Quantitative data was analyzed using statistical tools to identify trends and correlations, while qualitative insights were

derived from thematic analysis of interview responses. Secondary data from electoral records, scholarly articles, and government reports were utilized to contextualize findings. This methodology aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how religious identity influences political engagement and decision-making in the district.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table No: 1- Religious Composition of Respondents

Religion	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Hindu	40	61.54
Muslim	15	23.08
Christian	8	12.31
Others	2	3.08
Total	65	100

Source-Field Survey

Among the 65 respondents, Hindus form the majority with 61.54%, followed by Muslims at 23.08%, Christians at 12.31%, and others at 3.08%. This religious composition aligns with the demographic makeup of Tumkur District, where Hinduism is predominant. The inclusion of minority groups ensures the study's representation of the district's diverse religious landscape, contributing to a balanced analysis.

Table No: 2- Voter Turnout by Religious Group

Religion	Voted in Last Election	Did Not Vote	Total
Hindu	35	5	40
Muslim	12	3	15
Christian	6	2	8
Others	1	1	2
Total	54	11	65

Source-Field Survey

Voter turnout was high among respondents, with 54 out of 65 (83.08%) voting in the last election. Hindus had the highest participation at 35 out of 40, followed by Muslims with 12 out of 15, and Christians with 6 out of 8. Among the "others" category, only one person voted. This indicates robust political engagement among Hindus, likely due to their larger population and stronger mobilization efforts. The varying turnout among minority groups highlights differing levels of political inclusion and awareness.

Table No: 3- Influence of Religion on Voting Decision

Level of Influence	Hindu	Muslim	Christian	Others	Total
High Influence	15	10	5	1	31
Moderate Influence	20	4	2	1	27
No Influence	5	1	1	0	7
Total	40	15	8	2	65

Source-Field Survey

Religion significantly influenced voting decisions for 47.69% of respondents, with a high influence reported predominantly among Muslims and Hindus. A moderate influence was noted by 41.54%, and only 10.77% indicated no religious influence on their voting choices. These findings emphasize the role of religious identity and community narratives in shaping electoral behavior, particularly in regions with active identity-based politics.

Table No: 4- Gender and Voting Behavior by Religion

Religion	Gender	Voted in Last Election	Did Not Vote	Total
Hindu	Male	20	3	23
	Female			
Muslim	Male	7	2	9
	Female	5	1	6
Christian	Male	4	1	5
	Female	2	1	3
Others	Male	1	0	1
	Female	0	1	1
Total		54	11	65

Source-Field Survey

Gender analysis revealed that male respondents were more likely to vote (32 out of 39) compared to females (22 out of 26). This pattern was consistent across religious groups, with slight differences. While traditional gender norms may still affect women's participation, the relatively high turnout among female voters suggests growing political awareness and empowerment.

Table No: 5- Issues Prioritized by Religious Groups

Issues	Hindu	Muslim	Christian	Others	Total
Economic Growth	15	6	4	1	26
Social Welfare	10	5	3	1	19
Religious Harmony	8	3	1	0	12
Education	7	1	0	0	8
Total	40	15	8	2	65

Source-Field Survey

Economic growth emerged as the top electoral priority, with 26 respondents citing it as their main concern. Social welfare followed with 19 responses, while 12 prioritized religious harmony, and 8 focused on education. Economic concerns dominate the agenda across all religious groups, reflecting shared challenges such as unemployment and development needs. However, the emphasis on social welfare and harmony among minorities highlights their specific socio-political aspirations.

Table No: 6- Youth Electoral Participation by Religion

Religion	Age Group (18-25)	Age Group (26-35)	Total
Hindu	12	28	40
Muslim	5	10	15
Christian	3	5	8
Others	0	2	2
Total	20	45	65

Source-Field Survey

Youth participation was higher in the 26–35 age group, with 45 out of 65 respondents, compared to 20 in the 18–25 group. Hindus constituted the majority in both categories, indicating a strong political engagement among young adults. The lower participation among the younger cohort may point to challenges like apathy or lack of targeted outreach.

Table No: 7- Awareness of Electoral Policies by Religion

Level of Awareness	Hindu	Muslim	Christian	Others	Total
High Awareness	12	6	3	0	21
Moderate Awareness	22	8	4	1	35
Low Awareness	6	1	1	1	9
Total	40	15	8	2	65

Source-Field Survey

Awareness of electoral policies was highest among Hindus, with 12 respondents reporting high awareness out of 40. Across all groups, moderate awareness was most common (35 respondents), while 9 exhibited low awareness. This reflects the effectiveness of voter education initiatives but also signals the need for focused awareness campaigns among minority groups.

Table No: 8- Use of Social Media for Political Awareness

Social Media Platform	Hindu	Muslim	Christian	Others	Total
Facebook	18	8	5	1	32
Twitter	10	4	2	0	16
Instagram	8	2	1	1	12
WhatsApp	4	1	0	0	5
Total	40	15	8	2	65

Source-Field Survey

Social media played a significant role in political awareness, with Facebook being the most popular platform (32 users), followed by Twitter (16), and Instagram (12). WhatsApp had limited use for political engagement. These findings highlight the importance of digital platforms in shaping political discourse and their potential to influence younger, tech-savvy voters.

Table No: 9- Perception of Fairness in Electoral Process by Religion

Religion	Very Fair	Fair	Unfair	Total
Hindu	10	25	5	40
Muslim	3	8	4	15
Christian	2	5	1	8
Others	0	1	1	2
Total	15	39	11	65

Source-Field Survey

Perceptions of fairness in the electoral process were mostly positive, with 39 respondents considering it "fair" and 15 rating it "very fair." However, 11 respondents, predominantly from minority groups, found it "unfair," reflecting concerns about potential biases or marginalization. The overall trust in the system is a promising sign, though the dissatisfaction among minorities suggests areas for improvement in fostering inclusivity.

Conclusion

The study on the impact of religious identity on electoral politics in Tumkur District reveals key insights into voter behavior and political dynamics. The data analysis highlights the dominant role of religion in shaping voting decisions, with significant variations in political party preferences and voter turnout across different religious groups. Hindus, as the majority group, exhibit higher participation rates, while religious minorities, particularly Muslims and Christians, demonstrate distinct

patterns in their political engagement and party preferences. Economic growth and social welfare emerged as critical concerns for all religious groups, emphasizing the socio-economic challenges faced by voters. The study also emphasizes the growing importance of social media in raising political awareness, particularly among younger age groups. However, despite the generally positive perceptions of the electoral process, concerns regarding fairness persist, particularly among minority communities, suggesting room for improvement in fostering inclusivity and equity. Overall, this research highlights the intricate connection between religious identity and political behavior, offering valuable insights for understanding electoral trends and the factors that influence political participation in a diverse, multicultural society. The findings suggest that future political strategies should consider these religious and socio-cultural dimensions to enhance voter engagement and address the specific needs and concerns of different communities.

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WOMEN'S POLITICAL PARTICIPATION IN INDIA: AN AGENDA FOR EMPOWERMENT**Shantappa P. Hebali***Research Scholar, Dept of Political Science, Gulbarga University, Kalaburagi.**Email ID- skumar.hebali@gmail.com Mob- 8095686902***Dr. Chandrakant M. Yatanoor***Senior Professor & Chairman, Dept of Political Science, Gulbarga University, Kalaburagi.**Email ID- cmyatanoor@rediffmail.com*

Abstract

To promote women empowerment, enrichment in democratic governance is an essential requirement in any state or nation participation in political agenda and politics is essential in the development of good governance and democratic framework. In this regard, to increase the political participation of women, the most important institutions are the political parties. Political parties can influence women's political empowerment through Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) and international organisations. In India, women are still in a subordinate position in determining legislative and political priorities. In this backdrop, our study assesses the status of political participation that is playing a crucial role in achieving women empowerment; political participation; good governance. and women empowerment in India.

Keyword: *Women Empowerment; Political Participation; Good Governance. India, Agenda, Gender Equality*

Introduction:

Women's empowerment as a phenomenon is not something absolutely new. It has been there throughout history in almost all societies for a variety of reasons, What could be considered as new is its increasingly coming out in public, its having been shifted and reshaped from women's welfare to their development to now women's empowerment, and its being discussed, reported and critically evaluated. What is rather recent is the identification of the girl children and women as a special group and the acknowledgement internationally of the importance of specific focus on the critical and key issues related with the empowerment of women What is still more recent is the increasing realisation and recognition that empowering women is absolutely essential, rather imperative, for familial, societal, national and international development and progress. It has also been realised and accepted that genuine commitment and efforts have to be made by each country at the government, non-government and individual levels to work, towards establishing women's empowerment as nationally and internationally discussed also in UN World Conference on Women and agreed upon the Plan For Action. ¹

The first ever world conference on women was held in Mexico in 1975 to address the issue of gender inequality. It was followed by a second world conference on women at Copenhagen in 1980 and a third in Nairobi in 1985. At the UN Conference on Environment and Development in Rio (1992), world leaders accepted women's vital role in achieving sustainable development At the World Conference on Human Rights in Vienna (1993), governments acknowledged that women's rights are human and headed the evidence of widespread violence against women At the International Conference on Population and Development in Cairo (1994), women's empowerment was recognised as a cornerstone for effective population policies At the world conference for social Development in Copenhagen (1995), gender equality was recognised as a prerequisite for the achievement of productive employment, social integration and poverty eradication. The fourth world conference on women took place in Beijing in September 1995 followed by Beijing 5 held in Genva in 2000. ²

EMPOWERMENT: MEANING

Empowerment has become a fashionable and buzz word. It essentially means decentralisation of authority and power. It aims at getting participation of deprived sections of people in decision-making process. In other words giving voice to voiceless. Activists want government to empower poor people including women by legislative measures and welfare programmes. Unless capacity is built in these sections in reality, the power is used by others rather than the section for which they are meant.³

Empowerment may mean equal status to woman, opportunity and freedom to develop herself. The focus of empowerment is equipping women to be economically independent, self-reliant, have a positive self-esteem to enable them to face any difficult situation and they should be able to participate in the process of decision-making

Empowerment is the process by which the disempowered or powerless people can change their circumstances and begin to have control over their lives. Empowerment results in a change in the balance of power, in the living conditions and in the relationships,

EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN

The world over women are struggling to break the shackles that bind them and challenging the unequal distribution of power in society. Transforming the existing in egalitarian pattern of gender relationships necessitates leadership in the state, markets and civil society-the key centres of power in the present globalizing economy. It is, therefore imperative for women to be in the corridors of power and have the power to negotiate a better deal for themselves, if they are to influence policy decisions which have an impact upon them. Empowerment of women in all spheres, in particular the political sphere is crucial for their advancement and the foundation of a gender equal society. Women's political empowerment is premised on "three fundamental and non-negotiable principles (a) The equality between women and men (b) Women's right to the full development of their potentials, and (c) women's right to self-representation and self-determination. In empowerment, the key indeed is POWER' it 18 power to access', 'control' and make informed choices' To use an Indian expression, it is SHAKTI, which is manifested through the use of a mix of power, effectiveness, capability, force and influence to challenge and transform the structures and institutions of patriarchal ideology and existing power relations. According to the Jakarta Declaration. "Empowerment of women is not only an equity consideration, it was also a necessary precondition for sustainable economic and social development. Involvement of women in the political arena and in decision-making roles is an important tool for empowerment as well as monitoring standards of political performance." The application of the philosophical underpinnings of the Jakarta Declaration are necessary, because in the countries where women have gained near equal representation such as in the Scandinavian countries, they have begun to alter the very nature of politics.

EMPOWERMENT: A JOURNEY TOWARDS GENDER JUSTICE

Judicial activism in recent years had led to ensuring greater equality for women before the law. Review of legislation from a gender perspective has begun to bring greater equality for women. Greater awareness among women; a stronger recognition of women's rights, sustained public advocacy and effective judicial activism are beginning show some results. The Supreme Court's landmark judgement in 1997 on a writ petition by some women's groups seeking the enforcement of the fundamental rights of working women has paved the way for their greater protection from sexual harassment. The Supreme Court in 1997, also announced a set of guidelines for/sexual harassment for the first time. Court judgements have also started invoking international conventions like CEDAW to make a stronger case

for women's justice. Institutions like the National Commission for Women and the National Human Rights Commission are carrying out detailed investigations of injustices against women.

Women are, however virtually invisible in the political sphere. Under representation or invisibility of women in decision-making reinforces/their deprivation, leading to an unequal distribution of resources, neglect of their interests, needs, perspectives and priorities and now say in policy-making. Their voices fall in deaf ears, and as Alida Brill vehemently insists, "Without our own voices being heard inside the government arenas and halls of public policy and debate, we are without the right of accountability a basic entitlement of those who are governed."

ROAD TRAVELLED: FROM WELFARE TO EMPOWERMENT

In India numerous steps have been undertaken to provide constitutional safeguards and institutional framework for activities for women welfare. The development of women planning since independence. There have has been the central focus in developmental been various shifts in policy approaches during the last 25 years from the concept of "welfare" in the 70s to "development" in the '80s, and now to "empowerment" in the '90s. Now the emphasis is on the inclusion of women in decision-making and their participation at the policy formulation levels. ⁴

The Government of India has declared the year 2001 as year for the empowerment of women, but the struggle to reach this stage has been long and arduous. The concern for women's political equality in India first emerged as a political issue during the national movement in which women were active participants. As early as 1917, Indian women raised the issue of representation in politics, which at a time meant a demand for universal adult franchise. By 1929 women had the right to vote on the basis of wifehood, property and education. Under the Government of India Act, 1935, all women over 21 could vote provided they fulfilled the conditions of property and education. Post-independence, women continued to play a significant role in less conventional political activities such as environmental movement, anti-alcohol agitation, peace movement and even revolutionary activities, which equally affect power relationships as they have the capacity to influence the state. Yet, politics proved to be a very inhospitable terrain for women and continues to be the male bastion into which the entry of women is severely restricted.

Women's Political Participation

- Women's representation in political spheres improved in the latter half of the 20th century, with significant progress made in many nations in securing voting rights and parliamentary seats, and in climbing to the highest political offices.
 - New Zealand extended universal suffrage to women in 1893.
 - Norway first saw women enter parliament in 1907
- As of 10 January 2024, there are 26 countries where 28 women serve as Heads of State and/or Government.
 - 15 countries have a woman Head of State, and 16 countries have a woman Head of Government
- First-time compiled data by UN Women show that women represent 22.8 percent of Cabinet members heading Ministries, leading a policy area as of 1 January 2023 .

Status in india

- India has a history of marginalisation and exploitation of women framed by patriarchal social structures and mindsets.

- Beginning in the 19th century, social reform movements succeeded in pushing for women's well-being and empowerment.
- The Indian freedom movement, starting with the swadeshi in Bengal (1905-08) also witnessed the impressive participation of women,] who organised political demonstrations and mobilised resources, as well as occupied leadership positions in those movements.
- Women representation in Lok Sabha has increased from 5% in the first Lok Sabha to 15% in the current Lok Sabha.
 - Scandinavian countries such as Sweden and Norway, and South Africa have more than 45% women representation in their national legislatures.
 - Currently, 15% of Lok Sabha MPs and 13% of Rajya Sabha MPs are women.

Importance

- Women's equal participation and leadership in political and public life are essential to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals by 2030.
- Women's representation in the national parliament is a key indicator of the extent of gender equality in parliamentary politics.
- It will ensure that women form a strong lobby in Parliament to fight for issues that are often ignored.
- There is now evidence that women as panchayat leaders have shattered social myths, been more accessible than men, controlled the stranglehold of liquor, invested substantially in public goods such as drinking water, helped other women express themselves better, reduced corruption, prioritised nutrition outcomes, and changed the development agenda at the grassroots level.
- India has a high percentage of crimes against women, low participation of women in the workforce, low nutrition levels and a skewed sex ratio.
 - To address all these challenges, it is argued, we need more women in decision-making.
- The rate at which women accumulate assets while in office is 10 percentage points lower, per year than among men.

CONCLUSIONS

Women Empowerment helps to make the society and world a better place to live in and march forward on way to inclusive participation. It means increase happiness for the family and the organizations where women make a difference.

It can be conclusively stated that there has been a radical change in the movement for empowerment of women. Recognition is dawning that women are indeed becoming a ed political force, both nationally and internationally. In this context it would be noteworthy to recall the observations of Nobel Laureate Amartya Sen in his book, "India: Economic Development and Social Opportunity", "Women's empowerment can positively influence the lives not only of women themselves but also of men, and of course, those of children."

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ECONOMIC DISPARITIES AND ITS POLITICAL INFLUENCE ON THE STATE**Dr. Venkatachalapathi H S**

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Abstract

Economic disparities represent significant differences in wealth, income, and access to resources across various individuals, communities, and regions. These disparities are shaped by factors such as education, employment, healthcare access, globalization, technology, and government policies. The consequences of economic inequality can be profound, impacting social mobility, economic stability, and overall well-being. Widening economic gaps can lead to increased social and political tensions, as well as hinder economic growth. Addressing these disparities requires comprehensive policy solutions, including progressive taxation, investment in education and healthcare, and social safety nets, though the effectiveness of such measures can vary widely across different contexts.

Introduction:

Economic disparities, or inequalities in wealth, income, and resource distribution, have long been a fundamental challenge for societies around the world. The gap between the affluent and those with limited means has significant implications, influencing access to essential resources such as quality education, healthcare, and employment opportunities. This unequal access often limits individuals' ability to improve their socioeconomic status, perpetuating a cycle of poverty for certain groups or regions.

Economic disparities are shaped by a variety of interconnected factors. Education, for example, serves as a foundation for economic advancement, yet not everyone has access to the same quality of schooling or training. Similarly, labor markets are often segmented, with higher-paying jobs available to some but not others, resulting in stark income differences. Additional factors, such as healthcare inequities, the impact of globalization and technological advances, and government policies around taxation and social welfare, all contribute to widening gaps.

Review of literature:**Theoretical Foundations**

- Classical economic theories, such as those proposed by Adam Smith, Karl Marx, and later by John Maynard Keynes, have laid the groundwork for understanding economic disparities. Smith's "invisible hand" theory suggested that free markets could, in theory, balance inequality, but Marx emphasized the inevitable concentration of wealth among the capitalist class, leading to worker exploitation and economic inequality. Keynes argued for government intervention as a way to address economic instability and reduce income inequality, forming the basis of many modern welfare policies. More recent economists, such as Thomas Piketty, highlight that unchecked capitalism and limited redistribution efforts exacerbate income and wealth gaps over time.

Income Inequality and Economic Growth

- Research on the relationship between income inequality and economic growth has shown mixed results. Studies by Barro (2000) and Forbes (2000) suggest that inequality can spur growth by incentivizing investment and innovation, particularly in developing economies. However, other studies, such as those by Stiglitz (2012) and Ostry et al. (2014), argue that high inequality can

stunt long-term growth by limiting economic opportunities for low-income individuals and concentrating wealth in ways that reduce consumer spending.

Education and Economic Mobility

- Educational access and quality are frequently cited as critical factors in reducing economic disparities. Research by Goldin and Katz (2008) underscores the role of education in bridging economic divides, noting that individuals with higher education tend to achieve greater financial stability and upward mobility. Chetty et al. (2014) have also shown that education quality and access to educational resources are closely correlated with economic mobility, as areas with more equitable educational access often see higher levels of social mobility.

Impact of Globalization and Technology

- Globalization and technological advancements have created a “winner-takes-all” economy that often benefits skilled workers and large corporations while leaving low-skilled workers behind. Autor et al. (2013) highlight the rise of “job polarization,” where high-skilled and low-skilled jobs grow, but middle-skilled jobs decline. Frey and Osborne (2017) emphasize that automation may worsen income inequality by disproportionately affecting lower-wage, repetitive jobs, suggesting that without policy interventions, technological progress could exacerbate economic disparities.

Healthcare and Economic Inequality

- The intersection of healthcare access and economic inequality is also widely studied, with researchers like Case and Deaton (2015) showing that poor health outcomes are both a cause and consequence of economic disparities. Lack of access to healthcare can reduce productivity and economic potential for low-income individuals, perpetuating the cycle of poverty.

Policy Approaches to Reducing Inequality

- Many scholars have examined policy measures aimed at reducing economic inequality, including progressive taxation, minimum wage policies, and social welfare programs. Piketty (2014) advocates for a global wealth tax as a way to curb excessive accumulation of wealth. Similarly, Atkinson (2015) outlines specific policies, such as guaranteed minimum incomes and increased social spending, as measures that could help mitigate economic inequality. However, studies also caution that poorly designed policies can have unintended consequences, highlighting the need for careful policy design.

Social and Political Implications

- Beyond economic impacts, researchers have documented the social and political consequences of economic disparities. Wilkinson and Pickett (2009) argue that income inequality correlates with higher rates of social issues, including crime, poor health, and reduced trust within societies. Further, high economic inequality can lead to political instability, as documented by Alesina and Perotti (1996), who show that extreme economic disparities can fuel discontent and political unrest.

Objective:

- To identify and analyze the primary drivers of economic disparities, including education, healthcare, employment opportunities, globalization, and technological advancements.
- To examine the relationship between economic inequality and broader societal outcomes, such as social mobility, health, education, and political stability.
- To assess the effectiveness of existing policy measures aimed at reducing economic inequality, such as progressive taxation, social safety nets, and educational reforms.

- To explore the role of globalization and technological change in exacerbating or mitigating economic disparities, with a focus on labor markets, automation, and access to opportunities.
- To provide recommendations for policymakers on strategies to reduce economic inequality, promote inclusive economic growth, and improve social welfare outcomes.

Merits:

- **Enhanced Understanding of Inequality:** It helps to identify the factors contributing to economic disparities, such as education, healthcare access, employment opportunities, and structural inequalities, providing a clearer understanding of how wealth and income are distributed.
- **Informed Policy Development:** The study of economic disparities informs the design of policies that address income inequality effectively. By evaluating the impact of policies like progressive taxation, social welfare programs, and minimum wage laws, the research helps policymakers create more targeted and efficient interventions.
- **Promoting Social Mobility:** Understanding the barriers to upward mobility allows for the creation of programs and policies that enable individuals from disadvantaged backgrounds to access education, employment, and healthcare, improving opportunities for social mobility.
- **Economic and Social Stability:** Reducing economic disparities can contribute to a more stable society by alleviating social tensions and fostering greater social cohesion. This leads to a more peaceful and equitable society where fewer individuals feel excluded or marginalized.
- **Long-Term Economic Growth:** By addressing inequality, economic disparities can be reduced, promoting a more inclusive economy where all individuals, regardless of their background, have the opportunity to contribute to and benefit from economic growth, leading to more sustainable economic development.
- **Global Relevance and Cooperation:** The study is not limited to individual countries but also provides insights into global economic inequalities. It helps guide international policies that promote fairer trade and development practices, contributing to a more equitable global economy.
- **Improved Public Health and Social Well-being:** Economic inequality is closely linked to poorer health outcomes and lower quality of life. Addressing these disparities can lead to improved public health and overall well-being, benefiting society as a whole.

Scope:

- **Factors Contributing to Economic Disparities:**
- **Education:** Analyzing how access to education, quality of education, and educational attainment influence income inequality.
- **Employment and Labor Markets:** Examining disparities in job opportunities, wage gaps, job security, and access to benefits.
- **Healthcare:** Investigating how unequal access to healthcare affects the economic well-being of individuals and communities.
- **Globalization and Technology:** Assessing how global economic integration, technological advancement, and automation influence economic inequality, particularly the widening gap between high-skill and low-skill workers.

- **Government Policies:** Evaluating the role of taxation, social welfare programs, and public investments in mitigating or exacerbating economic disparities.
 - **Impacts of Economic Disparities:**
 - **Social Mobility:** Studying how economic inequality affects individuals' ability to move up the social and economic ladder.
 - **Health and Well-being:** Analyzing the links between economic disparities and health outcomes, as well as broader social determinants of health.
 - **Crime and Social Unrest:** Exploring how high levels of inequality may lead to social tensions, increased crime rates, and political instability.
 - **Economic Growth:** Investigating the effect of economic inequality on overall economic growth, productivity, and development.
 - **Regional and Global Perspectives:**
 - **National Disparities:** Focusing on income inequality and economic disparities within individual countries, including both developed and developing economies.
 - **Global Inequality:** Exploring how wealth and income are distributed across countries, with a focus on the global north-south divide, and understanding the role of international trade, development, and foreign aid in addressing global inequalities.
 - **Policy Interventions:**
 - **Redistribution Policies:** Investigating the effectiveness of progressive taxation, minimum wage laws, and universal basic income as tools for reducing economic disparities.
 - **5. Social Safety Nets and Welfare Programs:** Assessing the impact of welfare programs, such as unemployment benefits, healthcare access, and housing support, in addressing economic inequality.
 - **Labor Market Policies:** Exploring policies aimed at improving job quality, such as labor rights protection, unionization, and skills development programs.
1. **Long-Term and Intergenerational Effects:**
 - Wealth Accumulation and Inheritance:** Understanding how inherited wealth perpetuates economic disparities across generations.
 - Cycle of Poverty:** Examining how economic inequality often leads to a cycle of poverty that is difficult for disadvantaged families to break.
 2. **Comparative Analysis:**
 - Cross-Country Comparisons:** Comparing economic disparities across different nations to identify best practices in reducing inequality and fostering more inclusive economies.
 - Historical Trends:** Studying how economic disparities have evolved over time, particularly in the context of major global events like the Great Depression, the rise of neoliberal policies, or the recent impacts of the COVID-19.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, economic disparities remain a significant challenge for societies worldwide, with profound implications for social stability, economic growth, and individual well-being. The root causes of inequality are multifaceted, stemming from factors such as unequal access to education, healthcare, employment opportunities, and the influence of globalization and technological advancements. These disparities not only affect the economic mobility of individuals but also have broader social and political consequences, including increased health disparities, social unrest, and political instability.

Addressing economic disparities requires a comprehensive approach that considers the specific needs of different population and region.

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THE ROLE OF KKRDB IN THE REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF KALYANA-KARNATAKA: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS.**Manik Raj S**

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Abstract

The Kalyana Karnataka Regional Development Board (KKRDB) was established to focus on the socio-economic development of the Kalyana Karnataka region, which includes Bidar, Kalaburagi, Yadgir, Raichur, Koppal and Vijayanagara districts of the state. The goal of the KKRDB is to promote regional development by addressing infrastructure deficits, improving livelihoods, ensuring better access to education and healthcare, and mitigating regional imbalance. Accelerating the development of the state's most underdeveloped region and achieving balanced regional development on par with the state's developed districts are the main goals of the KKRDB. Prior to this, the High-Power Committee on Redressal of Regional Imbalances under the chairmanship of Dr. D.M. Nanjundappa, also known as Nanjunadappa Committee, constituted by Government of Karnataka to study the problems of regional imbalances in the state and the recommendations were partly implemented. Although the KKRDB was established with admirable goals, like all governmental organizations, it has operational flaws and difficulties that can limit its ability to effectively achieve significant and long-lasting changes in the Kalyana Karnataka region. This paper mainly focuses on critically evaluating the role and working of KKRDB in the regional development of Kalyana Karnataka and to provide suggestions based on observations and findings.

Key Words: KKRDB, Regional Development, Kalyana Karnataka.

Introduction:

The issues of regional development and challenge to achieve socio-economic development is a universal problem. Addressing the problems of regional development imbalances is a more complex issue because historically they have been at the disadvantaged level. Kalyan Karnataka, while it suffers from some historical factors, is also at some disadvantage in terms of natural factors like low and inadequate rainfall, poor soil, low underground water potential and so on. In fact, there exists sharp intra-regional diversity and disparities too. While the Sub-region comprising of taluks like Hospet, Bellary and Gangavathi is endowed with rich water and mineral resources, there are talukas like Jewargi, Sedam and Chincholi where resources are inadequate. This region needs a proper regional plan with differential strategies of development.

The Kalyana Karnataka Region, comprising the seven districts of Kalaburagi, Bidar, Raichur, Koppal, Yadagiri, Bellary and Vijayanagara district stand testimony to the influences of Islamic architecture, as also that of the Rastrakutas, Chalukayas, Hoyasalas, and Vijayanagara empire among others. The rule of Delhi sultans, Bahmani dynasty, Mughal Empire, as also historical relics and monuments such as Dargah of Sufi saints, Sharanabasaveshwara Temple, forts and other important sites, along with the teachings of Basaveshwara and Sharanas, the region is famous for its assimilation of the various cultural and linguistic influences constituting a mini-India or 'Bharat' of its own, epitomising the 'Unity in Diversity' harmonious concept.

Objectives of the Research Paper:

1. To assess the functioning of KKRDB.
2. To critically evaluate the role and working of KKRDB in the regional development of Kalyana Karnataka.
3. To provide suggestions based on observations and findings.

Methodology:

The research paper is based mainly on sources collected from secondary data. Data collected from CAG Report on Performance Audit on Functioning of Kalyana Karnataka Regional Development Board, Karnataka Human Development Report-2022, and sources accessed through websites of kkrdb, Department of Planning, Programme Monitoring & Statistics Department, and Karnataka Monitoring and Evaluation Authority of Government of Karnataka have been analyzed. To identify the issue, simple statistical calculations has been performed with the help of secondary data.

History, Organization and Functions of KKRDB:

The reorganisation of the state of Karnataka that characterised diversity in the levels of development aggrieved the people of Hyderabad-Karnataka region. Various commissions were established and scholarly research studies were conducted to examine this key issue of regional disparity. A committee was chaired by Dharam Singh in 1980 that led to the establishment of Hyderabad-Karnataka Regional Development Board (HKRDB) in 1992⁷. The Hyderabad Karnataka Development Board Act 1991 was repealed during February 2014 and the staff and other assets of the former Board was transferred to the newly constituted HKRDB. The board was renamed as Kalyana-Karnataka Regional Development Board (KKRDB) in 2019⁸. Through the 98th Constitution Amendment Act, the region was given special status under Article 371-J of the Indian Constitution.

The Board covers 42 assembly constituencies and has jurisdiction over the entire Kalyana Karnataka Region comprising of the districts of Kalaburagi, Bidar, Raichur, Koppal, Yadagiri, Bellary and Vijayanagara districts⁹.

The KKRDB is headed by a chairman and has 28 members on its Board comprising of Members of Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha, Members of Legislative Assembly and Council, Deputy Commissioners of the districts, Chief Executive Officers of the Zilla Panchayats under the Board etc. The Secretary, KKRDB acts as Member Secretary of the Board. The Board is responsible for execution of planned works through the Government departments/agencies and local bodies of the region. While the Member Secretary of the Board is primarily responsible for implementation of all macro projects, the Deputy Commissioner (DC) of the district/Chief Executive Officer (CEO) of Zilla Panchayat concerned are the nodal implementing officers for micro projects.

⁷ “Critical Evaluation – cum – Impact Study of the Report of the High-Power Committee on Redressal of Regional Imbalances with special reference to Hyderabad Karnataka Region”, Centre for Budget and Policy Studies, Bangalore, Sponsored by Hyderabad Karnataka Regional Development Board, Kalaburgi, 2018, pp 1-52.

⁸ “CM restores ‘Kannada’ pride identity with ‘Kalyana Karnataka’”, March of Karnataka, Volume-56 Issue-11 Page-28 Nov- 2019, pp 8-12.

⁹ Accessed through, <https://kkrdb.karnataka.gov.in/86/introduction/-en>

KKRDB has a mission of achieving rapid inclusive growth and balanced regional development with social justice for the Seven districts under Kalyana Karnataka Region¹⁰. The vision is to achieve this through Macro and Micro level planning by filling the historical developmental gaps in such a way that the centres of growth and the peripheries develop in tandems and in an interdependent manner.

The functions of the Board include¹¹:

- To ascertain relative levels of development in different sectors in relation to its Region, the basis of appropriate indicators having regard to the levels of development, State as a whole.
- To assess the impact of various development efforts in removing backlog and in achieving overall development within its region.
- To suggest the levels of development expenditure over the area of development board during a plan period including the annual plan.
- To suggest the Governor the 'policies' for the region which may have financial implications like incentives to be given to industries, private educational institutions investing in the region like tax holidays etc., and who also provide reservation in employment and in admission to educational institutions to the persons belonging to that region; within their financial limits.
- Prepare an annual report on its working and send it within three months after the end of every financial year to the Governor for placing it before the legislature.

The Role of KKRDB in the Regional Development of Kalyana-Karnataka: A Critical Analysis:

Art 1 of the Indian Constitution has declared that, "India i.e. Bharat is a union of states". It has a federal structure with more unitary features. A look at India's federal political economy clearly reveals that states and union territories are not uniform in terms of development. The inter-state/regional developmental disparity is grave and glaring. Hence it has been a major challenge for planning and policy making ever since its inception. Despite the implementation of many development programmes, regional disparities are persisting over time. There has been a huge gap between active and vibrant region and hinterland during the pre-independence period in terms of availability of facilities. This itself manifests unequal level of development. In this context, there is a necessity for not only of proper planning but also a dedicated developmental board for its enforcement.

The core functions of the Board towards redressal of regional disparities and ensuring balanced regional development was not discharged by the Board during the entire nine years (2013-14 to 2021-22) of its existence. The works planned and executed by the Board were not aligned to the indicators used for measuring regional imbalances and focused more on providing road connectivity. During last five years, the Board has spent 74 per cent of the released amount with physical progress achieved up to 70 per cent.

The Performance Audit of KKRDB which was undertaken by CAG to assess the effectiveness of the functioning of the Board in uplifting the Kalyana Karnataka Region in accordance with the responsibilities bestowed upon it by the Article 371-J and the Board Order 2013, has found major loopholes.

¹⁰ Accessed through, <https://demo.karnataka.gov.in/kkrdb/public/87/our-mission/en>

¹¹ CAG Report on "Performance Audit on Functioning of Kalyana Karnataka Regional Development Board", Government of Karnataka, Report No. 10, 2022, pp 42.

Details of Funds allocated to KKRDB (from 2013-14 to 2024-25)

Year	Allocated Funds (in Crores)	Released (in Crores)	Expenditure (in Crores)	Percentage of Fund utilisation against Allocated Fund
2013-14	Rs. 153.50	Rs. 78.97	Rs. 26.66	17.36%
2014-15	Rs. 600	Rs. 300	Rs. 322.59	53.76%
2015-16	Rs. 1000	Rs. 750	Rs. 493.66	49.36%
2016-17	Rs. 1000	Rs. 750	Rs. 960.02	96.02%
2017-18	Rs. 1000	Rs. 800	Rs. 450.32	45.03%
2018-19	Rs. 1000	Rs. 1000	Rs. 1193.54	119.34%
2019-20	Rs. 1500	Rs. 1125	Rs. 1246.81	83.12%
2020-21	Rs. 1131.86	Rs. 1031.86	Rs. 925.81	81.79%
2021-22	Rs. 1492.97	Rs. 1492.97	Rs. 1129.66	75.66%
2022-23	Rs. 2900	Rs. 2900	Rs. 1584.30	54.63%
2023-24	Rs. 3000	Rs. 3000	Rs. 2009.53	66.98%
2024-25	Rs. 5000*	Rs. 5000	Rs. 858.32	--
Total	Rs. 19778.33	Rs. 13228.80	Rs. 11201.22	56.63%

Source: Prajavani, Sept 17, 2024.

*Recent cabinet meeting held at Kalaburagi on Sept 17, 2024.

The above table presents the details of funds allocated to KKRDB from 2013-14 to 2024-25. It is found that, out of a total of Rs. 19778.33 cr allocated from the state government from financial year 2013-14 to 2024-25, the board has incurred expenditure of only Rs. 11201.22 cr which constitutes 56.63% which accounts only half of the expenditure incurred against the total allocated fund. This shows the inefficiency on the part of KKRDB with respect to fund utilisation for various developmental activities. It should be noted that, there has been two-fold increase in the allocation of budget to KKRDB since 2022, and the recent cabinet meeting held at Kalaburagi eventually led to the sanction of Rs 5000 crore¹², but the board due to its poor planning and execution of plans, and the boards dependency on departments and Zilla Panchayats for implementation, slow administrative decisions, size of the committee, lack of decentralisation within the board are few of the impediments on proper and non-utilization of funds allocated to it.

Year-wise details of works taken up by Board

Year	Total works taken up	Completed	Under progress	Not started	Cancelled
2013-14	782	597	0	0	185
2014-15	2523	1852	3	0	668
2015-16	4359	3256	19	0	1084
2016-17	3547	2893	17	0	637
2017-18	5142	4351	5	0	736
2018-19	4377	3799	334	24	220
2019-20	4239	2729	1106	208	196
2020-21	2215	43	779	1388	5
2021-22	854	0	39	815	0
Grand Total	28,038	19,520	2,435	2,352	3,731

Source: CAG Report on Performance Audit on Functioning of KKRDB, 2022, Table 4.1.

¹² "Big Bonanza for Kalyana Karnataka Development", March of Karnataka, Volume-31, issue- 10, October 2024, pp 11-18.

The above table specifically presents the details of works taken up by KKRDB for 9 years from 2013-14 to 2021-22. It can be laid down that, out of a total of 28,038 works taken up, the board has completed 19,520 works which constitutes 69.62% of the total works taken up. Moreover, 2,352 works constituting 8% of total works taken up were not commenced even after one to three years of approval. Besides, 3,731 works (13%) were cancelled during the period 2013-14 to 2020-21. This is indicative of the fact that the works were proposed and approved without any realistic need analysis and planning for development of backward region was deficient¹³. This clearly establishes the fact that, the need for adequate prior-planning before proposing the works for execution as the action plans should have been approved taking into consideration the needs and feasibility of undertaking the works.

The Board has adopted 'Taluk' as a unit under 'Micro, and under 'Macro' the 'District' is considered as a unit and grants have been distributed on the basis of Taluka CDI and district CDI wise respectively¹⁴. All developmental works are allocated taluk and district wise for the sanction of various micro and macro projects.

District-wise Fund allocation for Micro & Macro projects (2014-2018)

Micro Projects				
Districts	No. of works sanctioned	Fund allocated by KKRDB (in Lakh)	Percentage	Expenditure incurred (in Lakh)
Kalaburagi	3106	66942.77	29.93%	47750
Raichur	1451	39249.87	17.55%	25837.92
Koppal	1421	29661.61	13.26%	23581.84
Bellary	1320	27289.19	12.20%	19849.53
Yadgir	1203	27289.19	12.20%	19849.53
Bidar	903	33210.49	14.84%	24321.64
Total	9404	223,643.12		161,190.46
Macro Projects				
Kalaburagi	1425	68829.51	41.93%	37571.37
Raichur	294	20283.02	12.35%	7233.15
Bidar	409	22775.73	13.87%	12957.81
Koppal	246	18913.39	11.52%	9236.42
Bellary	560	18148.14	11.05%	7786.05
Yadgir	375	15168.56	9.24%	8101.97
Total	3309	164,118.35		82886.77

Source: VijayKarnataka, December 11, 2018, Page-03.

From the above table, it can be observed that, Kalaburagi has a lion's share in the sanction of both micro and macro projects as well as in fund allocation by KKRDB. During 2014 to 2018, Kalaburagi has a sanction of total 4531 works for both micro and macro projects, with a percentage fund allocation of 29.93% and 41.93% respectively which is much higher compared to other districts of the region. Yadgiri district has the least allocation of fund of 12.20% for micro and 9.24% for macro projects. The table presents major concern, that certain districts or areas within the Kalyana Karnataka region are receiving disproportionate funding or attention based on political representation, influence rather than on merit or need. This could exacerbate existing regional inequalities and also widen sub-regional disparities.

¹³ CAG Report on "Performance Audit on Functioning of Kalyana Karnataka Regional Development Board", Government of Karnataka, Report No. 10, 2022, pp 61-62.

¹⁴ Accessed through, <https://demo.karnataka.gov.in/kkrdb/public/87/our-mission/en>

One of the major challenges facing the KKRDB is the consistent underfunding of sectors that could address significant developmental gaps. The table below presents various 'Developmental' works under taken sectoral wise by KKRDB from 2013-14 to 2021-22 for 9 years.

Sector wise Allocation and Expenditure by the Board from 2013-14 to 2021-22(in Crore)

Sector	Allocation	Expenditure
Roads and Bridges	4,480.55	3,074.28
Education	2,137.70	1,287.74
Health	599.37	350.35
Water Supply	302.16	150.83
Women & Child	132.19	68.77
Urban Infrastructure	122.93	88.84
Social Welfare	188.11	127.18
Sports	73.03	12.72
Sanitation	71.57	36.99
Major Infrastructure	71.51	43.65
Irrigation	49.87	16.21
OBC and Minorities	47.68	32.89
Transport	39.57	11.41
Library	32.26	19.36
Employment	7.09	2.64
Agriculture	6.40	3.56
Others	492.88	273.63

Source: CAG Report on Performance Audit on Functioning of KKRDB, 2022, Appendix 3.5.

It can be observed that, fund allocation for the sector 'Roads and Bridges' which constitutes 51.05% forms the major portion of developmental allocation. Whereas, allocation of funds for social sectors like 'Education' and 'Health' which is 2,137.70cr and 599.37cr constituting a meagre 24.35% and 6.83% respectively has gained less importance in the progress of the region. The most neglected sector in fund allocation by the board are the sectors of Health, Women & Child. Fund allocation for Women & Child development was a meagre 1.51% of the total allocation.

This attitude on the part of KKRDB in unequal distribution of funds has brought the performance of the region in social sectors worsening till date. The recent Karnataka HDI Report 2022 also puts the districts of the region among lower ranking districts in social sector indicators.

In the Karnataka Human Development Index 2022, the districts of Raichur, Kalaburagi, Yadgir, with a HDI value of 0.562, 0.539, 0.538 stands among the bottom ten districts with HDI rank of 28, 29 and 30 respectively. The two districts of this region- Raichur and Yadgir are at the bottom of human development in the State and are in the category of 115 aspirational districts in the country¹⁵.

Raichur with a health index of 0.742, education index of 0.448 and income index of 0.535 together contributing to a HDI index of 0.562, ranks 28th, whereas Kalaburagi with a health index of 0.726, education index of 0.42 and income index of 0.514 together contributing to a HDI index of 0.539, is placed 29th below Raichur district¹⁶.

¹⁵ *Karnataka Human Development Report-2022- Bridging the gaps towards sustainable wellbeing*, Planning, Programme Monitoring and Statistics Department, Government of Karnataka, pp 4-6.

¹⁶ *ibid*

In the Multi-Dimensional Poverty Index for Districts 2019-20, the four districts of Kalyana- Karnataka region- Yadgir, Kalburagi, Raichur and Koppal as well as Bellary are at the bottom in the State. These along with Bidar, are placed in red zone and need focused approach with a package of schemes to address the deprivations in health, education and quality of life. In Malnourishment, at the district level, Kalaburagi, Raichur, Yadgir, Koppal are the districts with high incidence of malnourished children and anaemic women.

The Government of Karnataka in the year 2000 had constituted a high-powered committee headed by Prof. Nanjundappa to study the regional imbalances in the state and recommend strategies for their elimination. The committee had identified 35 indicators to measure the level of development under various sectors and developed a broad Composite development index (CDI). All the taluks are classified as Most Backward, More Backward, Backward. Among the taluks of Kalyana Karnataka region, 22 taluks are classified as most backward, 5 taluks as very backward and 2 taluks as backward taluks.

The KKRDB was also required to ascertain the relative levels of development in different sectors with reference to appropriate indicators, which it did not collect for analysis. But in the absence of any data with the Board, it could not contribute to the policy formulation aimed at accelerating the pace of development in the region. Consequently, the per capita income, health and nutritional status, educational performance of the KK Region continue to remain lower indicating the need for accelerating the interventions in these areas¹⁷.

One of the major drawbacks of the Board is that it has a mandate for redressing the regional imbalances under the Article 371-J of the Constitution which it did not articulate any strategic direction by way of drawing up a long-term plan for redressal of regional imbalances. The Board Order 2013 requires it to complete the planning process well before September of the previous year, but preparation of annual action plans were delayed every year as the planning process started only after the announcement of the allocation of funds in the State budget¹⁸. The plans prepared by the Board did not specify any targets to be achieved in respect of various socio-economic indicators, timelines for completion etc. Large number of works were cancelled or changed after finalisation of the plans pointing to inadequate preparatory activities before proposing the projects. Below is the table showing year wise date of submission of action plans by KKRDB to government and the extent of delay incurred for that purpose.

Year wise date of submission of action plans to Government

Sl. No.	Year	Due date of Submission	Date of Submission	Delay
1	2016-17	30/09/2015	23/03/2016	5 Months
2	2017-18	30/09/2016	23/01/2017	3 Months
3	2018-19	30/09/2017	07/08/2018	10 months
4	2019-20	30/09/2018	30/04/2019	6 months
5	2020-21	30/09/2019	13/07/2020	9 months

Source: CAG Report on Performance Audit on Functioning of KKRDB, 2022, Table 3.2.

¹⁷ CAG Report (Executive Summary) on “Performance Audit on Functioning of Kalyana Karnataka Regional Development Board”, Government of Karnataka, Report No. 10, 2022, pp 7.

¹⁸ Dr T.R Chandrashekhar, “Regional Developmental disparity in Karnataka- with Statistics and Observations”, one Day Seminar on the ‘Progress of Kalyana Karnataka and the implementation of Art 371 J’, jointly organised by Kalyana Karnataka Horata Samithi and Sharanabasveshwara University, Kalaburagi, Sept 16, 2024.

According to the findings of the CAG Audit report on functioning of KKRDB, the per capita income, health and nutritional status, educational performance of the KK Region continue to remain lower, as the board has failed to ascertain the relative levels of development in different sectors with reference to appropriate indicators, which it did not collect for analysis. In the absence of any such data with the Board, it could not contribute to the policy formulation aimed at accelerating the pace of development in the region. Moreover, it focused more on providing road connectivity in the region while the sectors such as education, agriculture, health, skill development etc., did not receive adequate coverage.

One of the major drawbacks of the various developmental works undertaken by the board was that the works were proposed without preparatory work such as acquisition of land, soil test etc., resulting in cancellation of works, change of works and delay in commencement of the works. This eventually led to large number of works being delayed from their timelines, and a majority of works being declared completed with nil or partial expenditure indicating inaccurate reporting of completion of works without ensuring its due completion. As discussed earlier (Table 4.1, CAG Audit report), and according to a recent state government release, so far 35,885 projects have been taken up and 27,264 completed, with 8,621 projects in progress¹⁹.

The monitoring at the apex level was inadequate as the Board did not conduct periodical meetings to discharge its functions. Non-appointment of Board members, non-constitution of Advisory Council, non-formation of Implementation Committee, non-constitution of Expert Committee are a few to be observed. The Board is yet to establish a robust quality assurance mechanism to ensure the quality of works executed by the implementing agencies. It had not undertaken any impact assessment of its works and a framework for facilitating public participation in monitoring of its works through social audits which was not established.

Observations and Suggestions:

The efficient working of KKRDB is the need of the hour. The board should not become only a fund allocating body. It should work in a systematic and time-bound manner. Although the state government is funding the board regularly and annually, the board has failed to fully utilize the funds allocated to it. It has often failed to determine and establish a mechanism for systematic allocation of funds received by the government. Instead of working as a 'Development Board', it is working on the principle of "Contract- Construction- Commission"²⁰. The board in its budget is allocating 50 to 60% of fund for Roads and Bridges and only 5 to 6% of funds to Health.

KKRDB should allocate 20% to education (primary), 25% to health and nearly 10% to women and child welfare out of its total budget. The allocation for roads, bridges and other physical works has to be met in state budget and the boards budget should not be utilized for the purpose. The budget of the board should not become an alternative to the state budget.

The board should conduct their board meetings regularly which it has failed to do so and prepare an action plan before the allocation of budget by the state government. Action plans should not be based on political considerations, but on the basis of actual merit and needs.

¹⁹ Big Bonanza for Kalyana Karnataka Development", March of Karnataka, Volume-31, issue- 10, October 2024, pp 18.

²⁰ Dr T.R Chandrashekhar, "Regional Developmental disparity in Karnataka- with Statistics and Observations", one Day Seminar on the 'Progress of Kalyana Karnataka and the implementation of Art 371 J', jointly organised by Kalyana Karnataka Horata Samithi and Sharanabasveshwara University, Kalaburagi, Sept 16, 2024.

Exclusion of Marginalized Groups such as Dalits, Adivasis, and women from the planning process has a risk that development benefits will not reach the most vulnerable groups in the region. Dalits and Adivasis constitute 35% of total population of the region as against 24% of the total population in Karnataka. Failure to address social and economic disparities could further perpetuate inequality.

Lastly, the board should realize that it is 'Development for the people and not People for the development' which matters. Long-term regional development requires building the capacity of local institutions and individuals to manage and sustain development initiatives. Without sufficient training and empowerment of local governance structures, the KKRDB's initiatives may fail to have a lasting impact.

Conclusion:

While the Kalyana Karnataka Regional Development Board has the potential to catalyze positive change in one of the most underdeveloped regions of Karnataka, there are numerous challenges and loopholes in its functioning that can hinder its success. Addressing issues such as political interference, poor financial management, lack of transparency, inadequate stakeholder engagement, and environmental sustainability will be crucial for ensuring that the KKRDB effectively meets its developmental goals and fosters long-term growth in the Kalyana Karnataka region.

References

DIVERSITY, EQUITY, INCLUSION AND THE IMPORTANCE OF BELONGING: UNITY IN DIVERSITY IN THE INDIAN SOCIETY

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Abstract

India is a terrestrial of unbelievable diversity, where unity thrives amongst a numerous of differences. With many states and union territories, and over a billion people, the concept of 'Unity in Diversity' in India is intensely deep-seated in the nation's ethos, reflecting the harmonious cohabitation of several languages, cultures, religions, traditions and civilizations. Unity in diversity is a term used to acclaim the sense of intimacy shown by individuals of the country. Celebrating what makes us all different and unique and the reputation of recognizing the constructive impact that diversity has within our families, our communities and our workplaces are the foundations of diversity, equity and inclusion. If we recognize diversity in all aspects, how does this recognition also celebrate the unity we strive for in this space? We hope that this article will allow everyone to see that unity and diversity are intertwined and makes us richer as we experience both.

Introduction

As we all know, India is a secular country. We, in India, are diverse in language, religion, culture, etc. Despite all these differences, there exists a remarkable sense of unity among us, which is why India is presented before the world as a nation that exhibits unity in diversity. India is a 5000 years old civilization and a land of rich diversity. Individuals from different religions live in peace and harmony. India is considered the best instance of unity in diversity in the world. India has also a history of being the oldest civilization in the world which dates back to thousands of years. India is home to 1.45 billion people and with many different languages are spoken. Some people follow different religions and cultural backgrounds and because of that India is considered a secular country. Despite the difference in caste, creed, and religion, Indians show a sense of unity among each other which could vary from celebrating each other's festivals or singing the national anthem with pride. That is why India is a land that shows unity in diversity.

What is Unity in Diversity?

Unity in diversity is defined as the concept of showing unity without uniformity and diversity without disintegration. It is used to show the unity between a group of individuals despite them being from different religions or cultures.

In India, there are nearly 1.45 billion people, and all of them share different thoughts and ideologies. The freedom struggle for Indian independence is enough to highlight the unity in diversity of our nation. People belonging to different religious and cultural beliefs unitedly fought in the movements for the liberation of our nation.

India is one of the world's largest countries and has people believing in various religions, and each of these religions has got its religious festivals. The people of India speak numerous languages like English, Sanskrit, Hindi, Bhojpuri, Punjabi, Marathi, Gujarati, Malayalam, Tamil, Odia, and so on. In spite of all these diversities, everyone lives in India with a strong love for the nation. It is this love that brings people together. It is never an easy thing to bring unity among these people. Nationalism and patriotism play a vital role in uniting the people of India. Unity in diversity increases the harmony and peace of a nation, and it shows the strength of any nation.

Unity in diversity is a phrase that signifies the unity among people with diverse cultural, religious beliefs, social statuses and other demographic differences. This phrase originated in ancient times and is used by various political and social groups to demonstrate unity among individuals or communities.

Unity in diversity can be stated as a conceptualisation for uniting people with different traits. The concept of secularism and unity in diversity has been used in our nation since time immemorial to symbolise the unity of people under one title India. The thought of unity in diversity helps individuals to accept people. People start respecting the individuality of living beings, value their individuality, and respect the opinions of the people. It develops a trust and connection between the people. Such coordination helps in effective decision making and aids in the growth of the nation. By improving mutual respect, solutions for various social issues, riots and other disturbances can be easily attained. It helps to decrease the hatred among the people and increases the overall serenity of the nation.

Historical Perspective and Cultural Influences and Diversity

India's history dates back to thousands of years, with abundant ancient civilizations prosperous on its soil. These diverse civilizations have left a permanent mark on the nation's ethos and inheritance. Over the periods, India has been a melting pot of various social influences, from the Indo-Aryans to the Mughals. This ironic history has given rise to a diverse and exciting society.

India's Diverse and Multicultural Society

Language Diversity

India is home to an amazing number of languages spoken, with 22 officially recognized languages and over 1600 vernaculars. Efforts to preserve and encourage indigenous languages are vital for maintaining India's linguistic diversity. Local languages are a vital part of India's identity. In many regions, it's common for individuals to speak numerous languages effortlessly. The multilingualism demonstrates the harmonious synchronicity of diverse linguistic backgrounds. This linguistic diversity is a evidence to the variety of cultures coexisting within the nation.

Religious and Spiritual Diversity

The root of Unity in Diversity in India is the sacred diversity it hosts. India is the origin of numerous major religions, including Hinduism, Jainism, Buddhism and Sikhism. It's also home to a substantial population of Muslims, Christians, and other beliefs. This sacred diversity has shaped India's ethnicity, values, traditions, and festivals. The country holds a gathering of beliefs, nurturing religious open-mindedness and unity. People from different faiths often come together to rejoice each other's customs & traditions. Festivals and traditions in India's calendar are filled with a plethora of festivals

Economic Power: India's diverse market is a huge fiscal benefit. Different regions contribute distinct products, skills, and services. This economic diversity helps in sustaining and growing the national economy.

Worldwide Encouragement: India's diverse population and culture have made it a global influencer. Its soft power, which includes music, films, cuisine, and spirituality, has captivated people worldwide. This influence helps in strengthening political and communal relations.

Political Constancy: India's diverse political landscape encourages compromise and cooperation making unity in diversity possible in India. Political power is often shared among different parties and regions, leading to a more stable and democratic governance system.

Communal Consistency: Despite the extreme diversity, India has a long history of social cohesion. People from different backgrounds often come together to celebrate festivals, share meals, and participate in community events. This social cohesion promotes a sense of belonging and togetherness and shows respect for one another's beliefs and practices. This social harmony is the bedrock of a peaceful and inclusive society.

Challenges Shaking the Pillar

India's diverse society faces numerous challenges, including poverty, caste discrimination, and regional disparities. However, it is the unity among its people that drives change. Grassroots movements, NGO initiatives, and social reforms showcase how diversity is a source of strength when harnessed to address societal issues. However, it is important to note that these challenges have often led to stronger bonds and a renewed commitment to the idea of a united India. The country has a history of resolving differences through dialogue and diplomacy, reflecting the resilience of its unity.

The journey of unity in diversity in India offers valuable lessons for the world. The ability to embrace differences and find strength in them is a model for harmony and peaceful coexistence. It showcases that a nation can thrive when its people come together, despite their differences, to build a better future.

India's strength in differences is the cornerstone of its unique identity. It is a shining example of how a nation can thrive by embracing its differences. In every aspect of life, from cultural celebrations to education and even in the face of challenges, we see examples of beauty of unity in diversity in India. By understanding and celebrating these differences, we can create a world where diversity is not a source of division but a reason for unity. India's diversity is a source of strength because it encourages cultural exchange, innovation, and resilience. It enriches the nation economically,

politically, and socially. Embracing and celebrating this diversity is a key aspect of India's strength and unity.

Significance of Unity in Diversity

Unity in diversity can be stated as a conceptualisation for bringing people with different characteristics. People can easily eliminate public challenges like discrimination and oppression from society with such concepts. Unity in diversity increases the harmony and peace of a nation, and it shows the strength of a nation.

Unity in diversity is essential for any country in the following ways:

For National Integration

Unity in diversity is very important for a country because it is easy to disintegrate people with different views and ideologies. If there is unity among the people despite their differences, it will always be impossible for a force to disintegrate the nation. The unity of citizens plays a significant role in maintaining peace and prosperity in a country.

For Development and Growth

Unity in diversity plays a vital role in the country's development because a country that is integrated will always move on the path of development. It will face fewer internal issues than a country that is socially unstable and divided on different terms.

For Peaceful Co-Existence

Diversity can also cause internal conflicts, but unity in diversity plays a significant role in maintaining peaceful co-existence with people with diverse cultures and backgrounds. It helps them stay united despite their disagreements.

How is India an example of unity in diversity?

In India, people are diverse in language, religion, culture, festivals, etc. Despite all these differences, a remarkable sense of unity exists among us. That is why India is presented before the world as a nation that exhibits unity in diversity. India is another brilliant example of Unity in Diversity. In India, people of diverse religions, cultures, castes, sects, etc. have been living together. Furthermore, they have been living together for many centuries. This certainly shows the intense tolerance and unity of the Indian people.

There is a great variety of climate, vegetation, wildlife as well as language and culture in India. In this diversity, there is unity. It is reflected in the traditions that bind us as one nation. People of all religions, creeds, castes, dialects, cultures, lifestyles, dressing sense, faith in God, rituals of worship, and so on coexist peacefully under one roof, i.e. in one country of India. We can never forget the liberation movements led by Indians of all faiths, religions, and castes to establish India as an independent country. In India, the struggle for freedom is a magnificent example of unity in diversity. Around 1.45 billion people live in harmony and contentment. With the world's second-largest population of numerous ethnic and religious groupings, India is now the most important secular country, with a distinct character of unity in diversity.

The Difference between Unity and Diversity

Unity:

- There is a feeling of togetherness and integration in unity. It is the spirit that holds people together and a bond that signifies a sense of fairness.
- Unity stands for relations between different groups that bind them into a single unit.
- Unity can also be defined as the absence of differences between people belonging to diverse classes based on religious, linguistic or racial aspects.

Diversity:

- Diversity refers to difference or differentiation. It can be defined as the collective differences of groups based on religion, race, language, etc.
- It is a diversity of classes and groups living in different regions, with different cultures, traditions and backgrounds.
- Diversity is a natural phenomenon that helps to bring different views, experiences and acceptance among people.

A family may have people with different views, interests, or preferences who show their diversity in many aspects, but they demonstrate a sense of unity among them as a family. Unity is a state of being, while diversity is a state of being separate or different.

Factors That Lead to Unity in Diversity

- ✚ **Geographical Unity:** This means unity around the geographical boundaries of the country.
- ✚ **Religious Unity:** Means unity among various religious groups, such as Hindu, Muslim, Christian, etc. All these religions have the same principles like kindness, honesty, the value of life, belief in an invisible power, etc.
- ✚ **Language Integration:** If there are many languages across the country, having a link language solves the plurality of languages.
- ✚ **Cultural Unity:** Means unity among various castes, sub-castes and communities. Despite the vastness, most ancient cultures have unity.
- ✚ **Political Unity:** A democratic system of politics that calls for political alliances at all levels.
- ✚ **Emotional Unity:** This means that there should be an emotional bond, and they should be close to each other.

Unity in Diversity in the Indian Society

India has been the best example to prove this concept for many years. More than 750 languages and tongues are spoken in India. People from different religious cultures and traditions live here. They follow different religions of their choice because India is a secular country. Being related to different cultures, languages and religions, people here respect each other and live with a feeling of love and brotherhood. There are about 28 states, and each state has its own culture, tradition and language. Despite such a difference, the people of India demonstrate a genuine sense of unity among themselves, which reflects the concept of unity in diversity. In understanding the concept of Unity in Diversity, we realize that we are all from different cultures, races, religions, genders, social-economic statuses, etc. Unity in diversity teaches us that these differences cannot keep us apart, and we are always better when we are united.

As we enter into Spring, enjoying the beautiful change in weather, where everything begins to come alive and bloom, you are encouraged to enjoy different festivals, museums, music, food, dance—all of the vibrancies that show our diversity while embracing the unity in enjoying these activities together.

Conclusion

Unity in diversity is a dream for many nations and organisations. In 2000, the European Union adopted “Unity in Diversity” as their official motto. The adoption of this motto highlighted the unity of diverse nations who were members of the European Union. This concept is integral for the betterment of human society. People have to develop faith in such uniting concepts. Then only can the world bloom in its full colours. People have to respect and love each other irrespective of their differences. With such virtues developed, people can easily eradicate civil challenges like discrimination and oppression from

society. Let's unite together and spread love for a better world. Let's embrace the co-existence of love, peace, honour and respect for everyone.

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THE ROLE OF JUDICIAL ACTIVISM IN INDIA'S DEMOCRATIC SYSTEM**Dr. Ranganathaiah C. B***BA., LLB., LLM., NET., PhD, Associate Professor of Law, Department Of Law, Government Law College, Kolar-563101*

Abstract

²¹Judicial activism in India has played a significant role in shaping the country's democratic framework, particularly in safeguarding fundamental rights and promoting social justice. This article explores the evolution, mechanisms, and impact of judicial activism in India's democratic system. Judicial activism is defined as the judiciary's proactive and interventionist role in interpreting the Constitution, enforcing citizens' rights, and holding government actions accountable. It gained prominence in India during the 1970s and 1980s, when the Supreme Court began to assertively interpret constitutional provisions, leading to the expansion of fundamental rights and the adoption of Public Interest Litigation (PIL) as a tool for addressing societal issues. Landmark judgments, such as *Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala* (1973), *Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India* (1978), and *Vishaka v. State of Rajasthan* (1997), exemplify the judiciary's involvement in protecting individual rights and addressing social justice concerns.

Through mechanisms like PIL, judicial review, and the broad interpretation of the Right to Life under Article 21, the judiciary has actively engaged in issues such as environmental protection, gender equality, labor rights, and privacy. The article analyzes the positive contributions of judicial activism, including its role in enhancing democratic values, promoting equality, and providing justice to marginalized communities. However, it also discusses the criticisms of judicial activism, particularly the concerns of judicial overreach, the potential disruption of the separation of powers, and the challenges it poses to the legislative and executive branches of government.

The article further engages with the ongoing debate on the limits of judicial intervention, emphasizing the need for a balanced approach that respects the roles of the legislature and executive while protecting constitutional rights. While judicial activism has contributed to the expansion of rights and social change, it must be exercised with caution to avoid encroaching on the responsibilities of elected bodies. In conclusion, judicial activism remains an essential feature of India's democratic system, but its future effectiveness depends on striking the right balance between judicial intervention and deference to the political branches of government.

This article employs a doctrinal research approach, case study analysis, and a review of relevant literature to provide a comprehensive understanding of judicial activism's role in Indian democracy. This analysis offers a nuanced perspective on the challenges and opportunities judicial activism presents within the context of a dynamic and evolving democratic society.

Keywords: *Judicial activism, Indian democracy, Public Interest Litigation, fundamental rights, judicial overreach*

Introduction:

Judicial²² Activism is a term that refers to the proactive and interventionist role played by the judiciary, especially in countries where the courts take an assertive approach to upholding constitutional values, protecting citizens' rights, and ensuring accountability in government. In a democracy, the principle of separation of powers allocates specific roles to the legislature, executive, and judiciary, with each branch functioning independently. However, judicial activism emerges when the judiciary steps beyond its traditional interpretative role, actively engaging in policy matters, interpreting laws expansively, and

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²² Judicial

occasionally striking down laws or executive actions that are perceived to infringe upon fundamental rights or violate the constitutional spirit.

In the ²³Indian context, judicial activism has played a pivotal role in shaping the country's democratic system. The Indian judiciary, particularly the Supreme Court, has often been called upon to resolve complex issues involving social justice, human rights, and governance. It has stepped in when the executive or legislature has failed to act on matters of national importance or when laws enacted by Parliament are seen as inconsistent with the Constitution. Judicial activism in India is most visibly manifested through Public Interest litigations (PILs), judicial review, and the expansive interpretation of fundamental rights. The proactive role of the judiciary has been instrumental in securing the rights of marginalized groups, ensuring environmental protection, and promoting gender equality.

While judicial activism in India has significantly contributed to the country's democracy by protecting citizens' rights and ensuring that the rule of law prevails, it has also led to debates on the scope and limits of judicial power. Critics often argue that an overzealous judiciary might overstep its bounds and intrude into areas reserved for the legislature and executive, potentially upsetting the balance of power essential to a functioning democracy. Nevertheless, judicial activism continues to be a key element of India's democratic system, frequently acting as a safeguard against authoritarianism and a force for social change.

This article explores the role of judicial activism in the Indian democratic system, examining its historical evolution, the mechanisms it employs, its impact on democratic governance, and the challenges it faces. Through an analysis of landmark judicial decisions and cases, we will explore the complexities of judicial activism and its relevance in maintaining the democratic fabric of India.

Review of Literature on Judicial Activism in India

1. Judicial Activism as a Constitutional Safeguard:

Scholars have widely acknowledged judicial activism as a safeguard for constitutional values, especially in protecting fundamental rights. In their works, such as Tushnet (1999) and Chandrachud (2017), authors argue that judicial intervention is vital for checking the abuse of power by the executive and legislature. In India, where the executive is often seen as overreaching, the judiciary's role in ensuring that laws and policies align with the Constitution has been considered a crucial mechanism for protecting democracy and human rights. The use of Public Interest Litigation (PIL) to address societal issues and uphold justice has been praised for increasing public access to justice.

2. Impact on Social Justice:

Many scholars have highlighted the role of judicial activism in advancing social justice, especially for marginalized communities. Works like Hickey (2004) and Singh (2012) emphasize that the judiciary has used its power to address social inequalities, such as caste discrimination, child labor, and the rights of women and minorities. Landmark cases like *Bandhua Mukti Morcha v. Union of India* (1984) and *Vishaka v. State of Rajasthan* (1997) are often cited as examples of how the judiciary has addressed issues where the legislature has failed to act, particularly in protecting vulnerable groups from exploitation and injustice.

3. Judicial Overreach and the Separation of Powers:

A significant body of literature also critiques judicial activism, particularly its potential for judicial overreach. Legal scholars such as Palkhivala (1984) and Subramanian (2007) warn that excessive judicial interference in policy matters can disrupt the balance of power between the branches of

²³ Indian context

government. These critics argue that the judiciary, though an important check on power, should not encroach upon the legislative function or undermine democratic processes by substituting its judgment for that of the elected representatives. The doctrine of "judicial restraint" is often advocated to ensure that the judiciary remains within its constitutional bounds.

4. Judicial Review and Its Role in Constitutional Democracy:

The concept of judicial review is central to the practice of judicial activism, and various scholars have examined its role in Indian democracy. Baxi (2002) and Krishna (2006) explore how judicial review allows the courts to strike down unconstitutional laws and executive actions, ensuring that no branch of government acts in violation of the Constitution. In their writings, these authors assert that judicial review is not just a right but a duty of the judiciary to protect democratic values, safeguard the rule of law, and ensure accountability in governance. The Kesavananda Bharati (1973) case and its interpretation of the Basic Structure Doctrine are often cited as pivotal moments that reinforced judicial review as a core function of the judiciary.

5. Evolving Interpretation of Fundamental Rights:

A growing body of literature addresses the evolving interpretation of fundamental rights by the Indian judiciary, particularly through the expansion of the scope of the Right to Life under Article 21. Scholars such as Desai (2014) and Mishra (2018) have examined how the judiciary has interpreted this provision in ways that go beyond its literal meaning to include a range of socio-economic rights, such as the right to a clean environment, the right to privacy, and the right to livelihood. This expansive interpretation is viewed as a means of adapting the Constitution to contemporary issues, making it more relevant to citizens' evolving needs in a modern democracy.

Methodology:

1. Doctrinal Research Approach:

This article adopts a doctrinal research methodology, which involves the systematic study of legal texts, statutes, case law, and judicial pronouncements. By examining landmark judgments, particularly those that have been pivotal in the development of judicial activism in India, such as Kesavananda Bharati, Maneka Gandhi, and Vishaka, this research evaluates how the judiciary has shaped the democratic system. Primary sources like judgments, constitutional articles, and PIL petitions are analyzed to understand judicial reasoning and the evolution of legal principles.

2. Case Study Analysis:

A detailed case study approach is used to explore significant instances of judicial activism in India. Cases like *Bandhua Mukti Morcha v. Union of India* (1984), *Vishaka v. State of Rajasthan* (1997), and *Puttaswamy v. Union of India* (2017) are analyzed to illustrate how judicial activism has been applied in various contexts, such as social justice, human rights, and environmental protection. This methodology helps identify patterns of judicial intervention and their implications for the democratic framework.

3. Comparative Legal Analysis:

The research compares judicial activism in India with its practice in other democracies, such as the United States and the United Kingdom. By examining how judicial activism functions in different legal systems, the study highlights both the similarities and distinctions in how courts interpret and enforce constitutional rights. Comparative analysis provides a broader context for understanding the role of the judiciary in protecting democracy, particularly in countries with a strong judicial review framework.

4. Critical Review of Literature:

A comprehensive literature review is conducted to evaluate existing scholarly works on judicial activism in India. Articles, books, and academic papers are reviewed to understand the theoretical perspectives, critiques, and debates surrounding judicial activism. This review forms the foundation for the analysis of judicial activism's impact on Indian democracy, as well as its potential risks and benefits, drawing from both legal scholars and political theorists.

5. Interviews and Expert Opinions (Qualitative Research):

To further enrich the understanding of judicial activism's role, qualitative research is conducted through interviews with legal experts, academics, and practicing lawyers. These interviews provide insights into the practical implications of judicial activism, especially about the functioning of the judiciary, the executive, and the legislature. Expert opinions are used to assess the balance between judicial intervention and the separation of powers, as well as to gather perspectives on how judicial activism is perceived in contemporary Indian democracy.

Historical Evolution of Judicial Activism in India:

The roots of judicial activism in India can be traced back to the 1970s when the judiciary began adopting a more assertive stance in interpreting constitutional provisions and taking a broader view of its role in upholding the democratic spirit. This shift was accelerated during the 1975 Emergency period when fundamental rights were suppressed, prompting the judiciary to take a more active role in protecting citizens' liberties. Landmark cases such as *Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala* (1973), which established the "Basic Structure Doctrine," served as turning points for the judiciary's interventionist approach.

Key Mechanisms and Instruments of Judicial Activism in India:

Judicial activism in India operates through several mechanisms:

1. Public Interest Litigation (PIL): PIL has been one of the most significant tools for judicial activism in India, allowing any public-spirited individual or organization to file a petition on behalf of those whose rights are violated. It has been instrumental in cases such as environmental protection, human rights, and social justice. The case *Bandhua Mukti Morcha v. Union of India* (1984), which addressed the rights of bonded laborers, highlights how PILs can bring issues of social importance to the judiciary's attention.

2. Judicial Review: The power of judicial review allows the courts to examine the constitutionality of laws and executive orders. The judiciary has frequently used this power to strike down legislation that violates fundamental rights or the "basic structure" of the Constitution, as in *Minerva Mills v. Union of India* (1980).

3. Expanding the Scope of Fundamental Rights: The Supreme Court has interpreted fundamental rights expansively, especially Articles 21 (Right to Life) and 32 (Right to Constitutional Remedies), to cover a wide range of issues from environmental protection to privacy rights. The *Puttaswamy v. Union of India* (2017) case, which recognized the right to privacy as a fundamental right, illustrates the judiciary's role in broadening the scope of rights.

4. Guidelines in Absence of Legislation: The judiciary has stepped in to issue guidelines on matters where legislation is lacking, often filling legislative gaps. A notable example is the *Vishaka v. State of Rajasthan* (1997) case, which set guidelines to address workplace sexual harassment until the enactment of specific legislation.

Impact on Indian Democracy:**Judicial activism in India has had several significant impacts on the democratic process:**

- **Protection of Fundamental Rights:** The judiciary's role in interpreting and expanding fundamental rights has strengthened the Indian democracy by enhancing citizens' rights and providing them with more avenues for justice. For instance, the expansion of the Right to Life to include clean air, water, and a healthy environment has promoted social welfare.
- **Accountability of Government Institutions:** Through judicial review and its rulings on PILs, the judiciary has played a crucial role in ensuring accountability of government institutions, preventing misuse of power by the executive and legislature. Cases addressing corruption, custodial violence, and abuse of power demonstrate this aspect of judicial activism.
- **Addressing Social Justice Issues:** Judicial activism has also played a vital role in addressing social inequalities and providing justice to marginalized communities. Cases such as *Indian Young Lawyers Association v. State of Kerala (2018)*, which allowed women entry into the Sabarimala temple, showcase the judiciary's commitment to social justice and equality.

Criticisms and Challenges:**While judicial activism has contributed positively to Indian democracy, it has also attracted criticism:**

- 1. Judicial Overreach:** Critics argue that judicial activism can sometimes lead to “judicial overreach,” where the judiciary crosses its boundaries, interfering excessively in legislative and executive functions. This criticism was raised in the context of judgments like the National Judicial Appointments Commission (NJAC) case, where the court struck down a constitutional amendment.
- 2. Impact on Separation of Powers:** Judicial activism challenges the balance of powers and the democratic principle of each branch operating within its limits. Excessive interference by the judiciary may hinder legislative and executive functions, leading to potential conflicts.
- 3. Concerns of Unelected Power:** Since judges are not elected representatives, judicial activism can sometimes be perceived as undemocratic or as the imposition of the judiciary's perspective on public policies. This raises questions of legitimacy and accountability.
- 4. Delays in Regular Cases:** The emphasis on PILs and activist judgments may contribute to judicial delays in regular cases, potentially impacting the justice delivery system as a whole.

Landmark Cases of Judicial Activism in India:**Several landmark cases exemplify judicial activism's role in shaping Indian democracy:**

- 1. Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala (1973) – Established the Basic Structure Doctrine, limiting Parliament's power to amend fundamental features of the Constitution.**
- 2. Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India (1978) – Broadened the scope of Article 21 (Right to Life and Personal Liberty), emphasizing due process.**
- 3. Olga Tellis v. Bombay Municipal Corporation (1985) – Recognized the right to livelihood as part of the Right to Life.**
- 4. Vishaka v. State of Rajasthan (1997) – Set guidelines for preventing workplace sexual harassment in the absence of specific laws.**

Conclusion:

Judicial activism has undeniably played a transformative role in shaping India's democratic system. Through its assertive approach, the judiciary has ensured that the core principles of the Constitution—especially fundamental rights and social justice—are preserved and expanded. The evolution of judicial activism in India, from its early days during the Emergency period to its more expansive role in recent

decades, illustrates how the judiciary has emerged as a critical safeguard for democracy, especially in areas where the legislature or executive has been slow to act or has failed to protect the rights of citizens. The judiciary's use of mechanisms such as Public Interest Litigation (PIL), judicial review, and its expansive interpretation of fundamental rights has allowed it to address a wide array of issues, from environmental protection and women's rights to labor exploitation and the right to privacy. These interventions have not only broadened the scope of individual rights but have also contributed to the socio-economic and political empowerment of marginalized communities. Landmark cases like *Kesavananda Bharati*, *Maneka Gandhi*, and *Vishaka* showcase the judiciary's vital role in interpreting the Constitution to address contemporary challenges, demonstrating that judicial activism is integral to maintaining constitutionalism in a rapidly evolving society.

However, judicial activism has not been without controversy. Critics argue that the judiciary, by stepping into areas traditionally reserved for the legislature and executive, risks undermining the democratic principle of separation of powers. Judicial overreach, where the judiciary may be perceived as substituting its judgment for that of elected representatives, poses concerns about the legitimacy of unelected judges making policy decisions. Moreover, the challenge of balancing judicial intervention with respect for the legislative process is an ongoing issue, especially in a vibrant democracy like India, where the judiciary's role must complement, not dominate, the actions of other branches of government. The tension between judicial activism and judicial restraint remains a critical area of debate. While judicial activism serves as a necessary check on the other branches of government, ensuring that democratic ideals are upheld the judiciary must exercise this power with caution. A measured approach that respects the limits of judicial intervention and defers to the legislature on matters of policy and governance is necessary to maintain the delicate balance between the branches of government.

In conclusion, judicial activism in India remains a double-edged sword: it is a powerful tool for justice, democracy, and social change, but it also carries the risk of overstepping constitutional boundaries. As India continues to grapple with complex legal, social, and political challenges, the judiciary's role as an active agent of constitutional protection will remain crucial. However, for judicial activism to continue serving the best interests of the Indian democratic system, it must be tempered by a recognition of the roles and responsibilities of other democratic institutions, ensuring that it acts not as a substitute for elected bodies but as a complement to them in the ongoing pursuit of justice and equality.

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WOMEN WITH DISABILITIES IN INDIA: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF KARNATAKA - CHALLENGES, ISSUES AND PATHWAYS TO INCLUSION

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Abstract

Women with disabilities in India face multifaceted challenges arising from the intersection of gender, disability, and socio-economic barriers, resulting in compounded discrimination and marginalization. This paper investigates the lived realities of disabled women in exploring critical issues such as healthcare, education, employment, violence, and accessibility. It also examines gaps in legislation, service delivery, and social attitudes toward women with disabilities. A focused case study of Karnataka highlights localized challenges and initiatives, offering pathways toward greater inclusion.

Introduction

“There is no hope of rise for that family or country where there is no estimation of women, where they live in sadness,” stated Swami Vivekananda, emphasizing the importance of women's well-being to societal progress. Gender inequality remains a crucial social issue in India, with women traditionally burdened by family and social responsibilities. Women with disabilities face “double discrimination” — both on the basis of gender and impairment — leading to underrepresentation in decision-making and marginalization (Mohapatra, 2021). Despite activism by women’s and disability movements, disabled women remain disproportionately excluded.

i) Data on Women with Disabilities in India

According to the 2011 Census of India, there were approximately 11.8 million women with disabilities compared to 15 million men, constituting 44.09% of the total disabled population (Government of India, 2011). Women with disabilities experience significant discrimination, including increased vulnerability to violence and exclusion from education, healthcare, and employment (Human Rights Watch, 2018).

Table .1- Data on Disabilities in India.

Residence	Persons	Males	Females
Total	26810557	14,986,202	11,824,355
Rural	18,631,921,	10,408,168	8,223,753
Urban	8,178,636	4,578,034	3,600,602

Source - Government of India Census, 2011

Cultural misconceptions and infrastructural barriers systematically exclude women with disabilities from full social and economic participation (Ghai, 2019; UN Women, 2021). Addressing these requires targeted policy and monitoring at all levels.

ii) Core Challenges and Issues

1. Lack of Educational Access

Women with disabilities face significant barriers in education due to inaccessible infrastructure and inadequate teacher training, leading to exclusion and neglect (Lalrinhlui, 2023). Many disabled girls are kept at home due to lack of mobility aids or supportive school environments, which hinders cognitive and social development (World Health Organization & World Bank, 2011).

2. Employment Discrimination and Inaccessibility

Disabled women face more severe employment discrimination than men, due to social prejudices and inaccessible workplaces (National Commission for Women & Society for Disability, 2007). Limited vocational training reduces opportunities for self-employment and economic independence (Mohapatra, 2021).

3. Domestic Violence

Women with disabilities are at heightened risk of physical and sexual violence, often by trusted caregivers or family members, which exacerbates mental health challenges (Human Rights Watch, 2018).

4. Health Risks

Although the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) protects the right to marry and have children, practical support remains inadequate (United Nations, 2006). Disabled women often face barriers to sexual and reproductive healthcare, increasing risks during pregnancy and childbirth (UN Women, 2021).

5. Inaccessible Public Spaces

Public infrastructure, including transport and healthcare facilities, remains largely inaccessible, limiting mobility and social participation (Centre for Internet and Society, 2022). This exclusion compounds social isolation (Comptroller and Auditor General of India, 2020).

iii) Case Study: Women with Disabilities in Karnataka

Karnataka has made strides in integrating disability issues within its development agenda and was among the first states to appoint a Disability Commissioner (Pradeep Kumar, 2009). The 2011 Census reported 1.32 million people with disabilities, with females numbering approximately 597,684 (Government of India, 2011).

Table -2, Data on total disabilities in Karnataka

Total Persons	Male	Female
1324205	726521	597684

Source: Government of India Census, 2011

Most disabled women (around 60%) reside in rural areas (354,089) compared to 243,595 in urban centers (Government of India, 2011). Rural women face compounded marginalization due to intersectional factors like caste and limited access to state resources (Ramesh Ashappa, 2018).

Table -3. Women with disabilities in Karnataka -2011 census -Urban and Rural.

Rural women with disabilities	Urban women with disabilities
354089	243595

Table -3 shown. that According to 2011 census, Karnataka women with disabilities, with a majority - 354089 nearly 60% of Female disabilities population living in rural areas compared to 243595 in urban areas.

Table-4. Summary of Female Disability Data in Karnataka (2011)

In seeing	130261
In Hearing	113006
In Speech	40893
In Movement	100843

Mental Retardation	44473
Mental Illness	10085
Any others	113642
Multiple disability	44481

As shown in Table -4. According to 2011 Census, Karnataka female persons with disabilities, among them, the highest number are suffering by Visual -In Seeing (1.3 lakhs), hearing (1.13 Lakhs) and Movements related disabilities (1 Lakhs), along with 44481 are suffer from multiple disability.

iv) Challenges Specific to Karnataka

Despite policy frameworks and inclusive schemes, women with disabilities in Karnataka continue to face systemic and infrastructural barriers that affect their access to education, employment, healthcare, and social participation.

According to comptroller and auditor general (CAG) report 2024- revealed that out of 51,464 regular schools in Karnataka, 20366 lacks ramps. 28843 have no handrails and 52000 are without toilets for disabled persons severally impacting accessibility for students with disabilities.

In raichur district, literary rates among disabled women were found to be around 7% lower than the state average,

Employment remains another major challenge and employment opportunities for women with disabilities are limited, Data indicates that only 23% women with disabilities are employed, compared to 47% of their males' counterparts with disabilities. Under MNRGA in Karnataka, out of 80 lakhs applicants, only 20000 persons with disability received employments is a significant gap in workforce inclusivity. (Rao, 2023)

A Study on health behaviours among women with disabilities in Karnataka found that while 80% sought care for health issues, many health care facilities lack physical accessibility and delayed treatment for women with disabilities. Women with disabilities sought medical care when ill, they faced delays due to inaccessible hospitals and clinics, particularly in rural Karnataka (Indumathi Rao, 2004; WHO, 2011).

Social attitudes and stigma further marginalize women with disability, cultural perception often views women with disabilities incapable leading social programmes.

Women with disabilities are subjected to stereotypes that question their abilities and worth, feeling of isolation impacting their mental health. To bridge these gaps, a multifaceted approach can move towards a more inclusive policy.

Despite welfare schemes like the Monthly Pension Scheme, Free Bus Passes, ADIP Aids and Appliances, Nirmala Health Insurance, and Ex-Gratia Financial Assistance, many government buildings, especially in rural districts like Raichur and Koppal, remain inaccessible. According to Human Rights Watch (2021), Panchayat offices and PHCs still lack ramps, lifts, and other accommodations. In Bangalore slums, dropout rates among disabled girls are high due to transport and infrastructure barriers (Samarthanam Trust, 2018).

The Department of Empowerment of Differently Abled and Senior Citizens (DEDASC) has played a vital role in providing financial assistance and employment support. However, the implementation of these schemes needs strengthening (Ramesh Ashappa, 2018). Several NGOs such as

Mitra Jyothi, Ashadeepa, and ADD India actively support women with visual, auditory, and locomotor impairments through braille transcription, vocational training, and community rehabilitation.

Karnataka has also made progress in legal frameworks. The state offers 3% reservation for Persons with Disabilities (PwDs) in Group A and B government jobs and 5% in Group C and D. In *Siddaraju v. State of Karnataka*, the Supreme Court upheld the right of PwDs to reservations in promotions, pushing further for equitable employment (Supreme Court of India, 2020).

Additionally, the Department of Women and Child Development provides financial aid to disabled women, including those who are visually and hearing impaired. The Karnataka State Women Development Corporation (KSWDC) organizes empowerment training for vulnerable women, including those with disabilities.

The state is also home to inspiring women with disabilities:

- Malathi Krishnamurthy Holla, an international Paralympian from Karnataka, has won over 397 gold medals and received the Padma Shri and Arjuna Award.
- Pushpa Preeya, a scribe for visually impaired students, received the Nari Shakti Puraskar for having written over 1,000 exams on behalf of disabled students.
- Rajalakshmi S.J., a paraplegic dental student, legally challenged norms to continue her MDS degree, proving that disability need not hinder ambition.

V) Pathways to Inclusion

1. Promote community-based collaboration to include disabled women in social and cultural life (Ghai, 2019).
2. Public awareness campaigns to dismantle stigma and recognize contributions of women with disabilities (UN Women, 2021).
3. Implement inclusive education with accessible schools, flexible curricula, and teacher training (Lalrinhlui, 2023).
4. Develop vocational training tailored to women's strengths and needs (National Commission for Women & Society for Disability, 2007).
5. Ensure accessible healthcare including sexual and reproductive health services (United Nations, 2006).
6. Improve infrastructure for transportation, sanitation, and digital accessibility (Centre for Internet and Society, 2022).
7. Support local self-help groups and community-based care (Mohapatra, 2021).
8. Strengthen gender-sensitive legislative oversight to ensure implementation of disability rights (Comptroller and Auditor General of India, 2020).

Conclusion

Women with disabilities in India remain marginalized and excluded, with their challenges compounded by intersecting social identities. Karnataka's experience highlights both progress and persistent gaps, illustrating the need for comprehensive, gender-sensitive policies and grassroots engagement. Expanding reservations in government and private sectors based on educational qualifications can empower disabled women economically. By enhancing awareness, infrastructure, and inclusive policies, society can foster an equitable environment where women with disabilities achieve their full potential and dignity.

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ISSUES AND CHALLENGES ON HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA SPECIAL REFERENCE TO KARNATAKA**Dr. Mamatha N***Associate Professor, Department of Economics, Government First Grade College, Kunigal**Email: drnmamathaminchu@gmail.com Cell: 9741032365*

Higher education refers to the level of education that follows secondary education and provides advanced academic and professional knowledge and skills. This usually includes bachelor's degrees and postgraduate programs such as master's degrees and doctoral degrees.

Challenges in higher education in India:**Registration:**

India's Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) in higher education is only 28.4% (2021-22), which is in contrast to other countries indicated. With the expansion of enrollments at the college level, there is a lack of infrastructure for higher education foundations to meet the developing need of the nation.

Equality:

There is no equality in GER across countries. As previous studies have suggested, GER varies to a more significant extent between males and females in higher education in India. There are some regional differences, with some states having higher GERs, while others are far behind the national GER, reflecting the large inequalities within the higher education system.

Quality

Quality in higher education is a multi-dimensional, bewildering and powerful concept. Ensuring quality in higher education is one of the first issues that India is seeing today. Whatever the case, the government is constantly emphasizing on quality education.

However, a large number of schools and universities in India cannot meet the basic prerequisites set somewhere around the UGC and our universities are not in a position to check their place among the top universities in the world.

Poor Infrastructure:

Poor infrastructure is another test for the Indian higher education system especially the poor physical equipment, offices and infrastructure are suffering the ill effects.

Political Resistance | Higher Education in India

Political promoters who have taken up the key job of managing the collection of universities are advocating for most educational institutions. They are exploiting the guilty understudies for their narrow-minded methods.

Student crusades are taking place, students are neglecting their own goals and are starting to build their careers through the law. The shortage of faculty and the inability of the state education system to attract and retain well-qualified teachers are presenting problems of quality education in India for a long time. The huge NET/Ph.D.

Even though there is a starting point in higher education, those who come up are unemployed, these qualified candidates are then applying to various offices, which is a big blow to the higher education system.

Accreditation

According to data provided by NAAC, as of June 2010, “25% of the entire higher education institutions in the country are not accredited in any way. Moreover, of those accredited, only 30% of the universities and 45% of the schools are of the standard to be ranked at ‘A’ level.

Research and Innovation | Higher Education in India

Our country has the most promising researchers, whose composition has been mentioned by famous Western creators. There is a lack of spotlight in exploring higher education institutions. There are inadequate properties and offices, restricted quantities of quality faculty to advise understudies.

The majority of examination researchers are uncooperative or do not get their associations on time, which impacts their pursuits legally or circumstantially. Furthermore, the foundations of Indian higher education are inadequately associated with inquiring about concentration. Thus, this is another area of challenges with higher education in India.

Structure of Higher Education

The management of Indian education faces the challenges of over-centralization, bureaucratic structures and absence of accountability, directness and polished approach.

Due to the increase in the number of affiliated schools and students, the weight of the official aspects of universities has expanded fundamentally and the central focus on scholars and research has weakened.

What are the types of higher education institutions in India?

There are various types of higher education institutions in India, including central universities, state universities, deemed universities, private universities and autonomous institutions. Each type of institution has its own governing body and regulations.

Popular entrance exams for higher education in India:

Popular entrance exams for higher education in India are the Joint Entrance Examination (JEE) for engineering programmes, the National Eligibility cum Entrance Test (NEET) for medical programmes, the Common Entrance Test (CAT) for management programmes and the Graduate Aptitude Test in Engineering (GATE) for engineering and science subjects.

Budget allocation in Higher Education in India

Expenditure on education as a share of GDP (Table 9) has been increasing in India from 0.64 per cent in 1950-51 to 4.29 per cent in 2012 (MHRD, 2014a). Public expenditure on education has been Rs. 170 million in 1950-51. Rs 60677 million in 2001-02 and onwards.

Finance Minister Nirmala Sitharaman, while presenting the Union Budget 2024, has allocated Rs. 47,619 crore for the higher education sector under the Ministry of Education. This is an increase of 8 per cent over the allocation in the previous year.

The University Grants Commission (UGC) budget is divided into three main areas: UGC itself, Central Universities and Deemed Universities.

Starting from the financial year 2024-25, funds for some colleges affiliated to Central Universities will be transferred from the UGC budget to the Central Universities budget.

This adjustment will lead to a significant increase in funding for Central Universities, from Rs 11,612 crore in the previous budget to Rs. 15,928 crore, while the UGC budget will see a cut.

Additionally, the budget allocated to Deemed Universities under the Central Government has seen a significant increase from Rs 500 crore to Rs 596 crore.

The UGC budget for the current financial year has increased from Rs 17,473 crore to Rs 19,024 crore, a significant increase of 9% over the previous year.

Finance Minister Nirmala Sitharaman presented the seventh consecutive Union Budget for 2024-25 in the Budget Session of Parliament on July 23. In her budget speech, FM Sitharaman highlighted key priorities aimed at boosting economic growth and creating opportunities, including employment and skills, and productivity in various service sectors. He emphasized innovation, research and development, and next-generation improvements.

Higher Education in India:

India's higher education system is the third largest in the world, next to the United States and China. The main governing body at the tertiary level is the University Grants Commission, which enforces its standards, advises the government, and helps coordinate between the center and the state. Accreditation for higher learning is overseen by 83 autonomous institutions established by the University Grants Commission. Indian higher education system has expanded at a fast pace by adding nearly 58,000 colleges and more than 43 million students in a decade from 2000-01 to 2021-22. As of 2021, India has 56 central universities, 459 state universities, 124 deemed universities, 90 private universities, 5 institutions established and functioning under the State Act, and 33 Institutes of National Importance. Other institutions include 100 exclusive women's colleges, functioning under these universities and institutions as reported by the UGC in 2021.

Challenges for Higher Education in Karnataka:

Localisation of the state university system.

Increasingly the state universities are becoming sites of academic inbreeding. Most teachers and students of State Universities come from the same or contiguous regions as the location of the University. Only rarely does a State University reflect a truly state-wide, let alone a national, outlook in the choice of faculty and students. This trend localises the Universities in a very debilitating way. One argument has been that the mandate of State Universities is to redress regional imbalances and provide opportunity for the youth of the region.

Lack of clear policy frameworks for entry of new education providers to the

higher education system: The next decade will witness a huge influx of private and foreign players into the higher education system in our country. Even now, private investment in higher education, especially in the professional courses, is exponentially higher than public investment. In Karnataka, private investment in both medical and engineering institutions is a little above 80% and public investment only accounts for the remaining 15 to 20%. Apart from the regulatory and governance issues regarding private institutions, it will be crucial to examine the terms on which new players, both private and foreign, will enter the system as also the scope of services they would be willing to offer, facilities they need to create, policy of enrollment, etc.

Lack of mission differentiation between several types of institutions Although the

higher education scene is variegated in terms of Institutional typology and responds to the diverse demands of many sections of the society, it is puzzling to note that this variety is not reflected in the differentiation in the mission of most institutions. All higher educational institutions irrespective of the differences in their location, demography specialization, core competences, financial strength, local resources and opportunities resort to highly stereotypical and straitjacketed modes of functioning.

Trust deficit of public in higher educational institutions. Despite the wide spread rhetoric about the importance and value of education and the respect commanded by an "educated person" in our social life, there seems to be very little translation of this sentiment into active public trust in our institutions of higher education. The decreasing role of private philanthropy in higher education and the increasing

mistrust in the value of a university degree, (demonstrated by many studies, which capture corporate house attitudes regarding the employability of fresh graduates) is a cause of serious concern

Lack of dynamic learning goals and curricular relevance Ask any student why he is in higher education and he will give you answers that are far from inspiring. Ask any graduate what was the use of his college education, he will most often than not go on a diatribe against his educational degree and its utter irrelevance to the demands of his professional or social life. A better way of articulating this problem is to say that students are unable to make sense of their education because they are unable to make use of their education. They are unable to make use of their education because their education is not inducing in them critical skills or meta-learning which includes the competence to " learn to learn. Most content-based education, added with the compartmentalization fostered by discipline-bound approaches is failing in the task of producing people who are capable of thinking creatively: a demand made on young people both by employers and advanced researchers.

Research Orientation in Higher Education. Lack of research culture at our Universities is the result of a number of problems that troubles the 17 University system No magical solution may be on the offer . However, certain concrete steps to encourage research culture in the universities beyond the present scheme of financial incentives needs to be explored. It is important to integrate research into the bloodstream of the university and not make it add-on.

Bridging the gap between school education and higher education : A crucial issue in Indian higher education is the quality and competence of school graduates who enter into the University system. Although in the recent years immense developments have taken place in school education reform, It has not always resulted in the increase in the gross enrolment ratio for higher education nor has it reduced the entry-level barriers to higher education. Contrary to this problem is that of benchmarking and gradation.

Last-mile problems in ICT for Higher Education: When most universities worldwide have successfully adopted ICT in higher education, Indian universities and colleges suffer from a plethora of last-mile problems in implementing ICT-based solutions. Most success stories in India in the implementation of ICT are localised to institutional cases and have not proved to be scalable across the entire spectrum of higher education. It is important to stress the need for internet and computers as a basic need comparable with basic needs like education and livelihood.

Academic Audit: Although academic auditing of higher education institutes is on cad it has not been regularly done. Wherever it is done, deficiencies mentioned in the report are hardly addressed.

Alternative Education for College Dropouts: At present higher education is a dream for those who temporarily leave colleges because of financial or other social problems. By the time, they overcome their difficulties it will be too late to pursue education. There are no other alternative avenues in our system to cater to the special needs of dropouts..

Prospects for Higher Education in Karnataka:

- Establish new universities and other institutions of higher learning in all disciplines, and increase the number of new and innovative Academic Staff Training Colleges and Interdisciplinary Centers for advanced research in Higher Education.
- Enhance infrastructural facilities and upgrade the existing ones
- Achieve 25 % of gross enrolment ratio by 2020
- Create an alternative system of academic audit along with the NAACINBA while increasing the percentage of universities and colleges under the NACNEBA accreditation.

- Peer review of the institutions to be made mandatory to know the strength, weaknesses and progression of the institutions
- Enhance research in terms of the award of doctoral, postdoctoral, D. Lit, degrees "and in terms of research publication. By 2020, we set the target of increasing the figure by 60 percent more (approximately 5000).
- Research output and patents from our universities to be increased considerably.
- Establish a permanent Academy for Higher Education on par with Administrative Training Academies to make teachers of higher education committed to the Profession
- Establish monitoring and facilitation cells for accessing UGC and other funding agencies.
- Bring out examination reforms to test the competencies and skills of students rather than their memory. Introduce the concept of continuous comprehensive evaluation, after carefully examining the required modalities.
- As an immediate goal, Karnataka State Higher Education Council shall set up a
- Higher-power Committee to review the vision and workout the strategies to adopt for vision 2020.
- A rigorous commitment to production and dissemination of new knowledge in a variety of areas of Inquiry.
- Accessibility to higher education not just in terms of entry-level support systems like reservations and fee-waivers but also additionally, continuous mentoring and capacity-building exercises for the benefit of students coming from the disadvantaged sections.
- Autonomy and integrity in relation to the working of the University such that it realizes the goal of the unencumbered pursuit of truth.
- Liberal and humanistic outlook which emphasizes the holistic development of the individual and society, fosters critical thinking and constructive participation in social and political processes
- A renewed investment in the figure of the teacher who embodies the virus of intellectual pursuits.
- Encourage and support the establishment of universities and institutes of higher. education especially in rural and backward areas

Conclusion:

The state-of-the-aspiration of the higher education system in Karnataka is rich but not ideal. From the perspective of transforming Karnataka into a knowledge society, , there is a rich diversity of institutions whose aspirations cluster in both predictable and unexpected ways, thus providing the basis for integrating a set of well differentiated institutions of higher into karnataka's knowledge ecology. Specialized and Comprehensive institutions are comingled in their aspiration, and so are Research, Private, State, Deemed, and National institutions. Such comingling can, on the one hand, be seen as the dilution of the institutions' mission and mandate; on the other, it may represent the evolution of the institutions and thus as an opportunity for integrating them into the knowledge ecology.

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UNDERSTANDING SOCIAL JUSTICE AND RESERVATION POLITICS: IMPLICATIONS FOR DEMOCRATIC PARTICIPATION IN TUMKUR DISTRICT

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Abstract

This study explores the intersection of reservation policies, social justice, and political participation. Using a sample of 50 respondents from diverse demographic backgrounds, the research examines awareness, perceptions, and the socio-political impact of reservation policies within the district. The findings reveal that 50% of respondents are fully aware of reservation policies, while 30% are partially aware. However, perceptions of fairness are divided—40% believe the policies are fair, while 30% view them as unfair. Regarding employment opportunities, 36% of participants reported positive outcomes from reservation policies, though 24% highlighted negative impacts. Caste-based electoral participation indicates that OBCs and SC/ST groups show higher engagement, with over 80% regularly participating in elections. Trust in political leaders advocating for reservation policies remains moderate, with 50% expressing moderate trust. Furthermore, the study finds that reservation politics significantly influences voting behavior in 40% of respondents. While 50% report satisfaction with government policies promoting social justice, others raise concerns about persistent discrimination, bureaucratic barriers, and lack of awareness affecting social inclusion. The data also suggest that access to government welfare schemes varies by caste, with OBC and SC/ST groups reporting higher participation rates. These findings emphasize the complexities of reservation politics and its dual role in promoting both inclusion and division. Overall, the study highlights the critical need for equitable policy implementation to foster democratic participation and enhance social justice in Tumkur District.

Keywords: *Social Justice, Reservation Politics, Democratic Participation, Tumkur District*

Introduction

India's democracy is built on the principles of social justice and inclusion, with the reservation system acting as a key mechanism to uplift marginalized communities. The primary goal of these policies is to ensure equitable access to education, employment, and governance for historically disadvantaged groups such as Scheduled Castes (SCs), Scheduled Tribes (STs), and Other Backward Classes (OBCs). Enshrined in Articles 15(4) and 16(4) of the Indian Constitution, these provisions enable the state to address structural inequities through affirmative action. However, the practical implementation of reservation policies has sparked significant debate, especially regarding their influence on political participation and social dynamics in regions like Tumkur District. Tumkur District, situated in Karnataka, exemplifies the complex relationship between reservation politics and democratic engagement. The region has a diverse socio-economic composition, with various caste groups, including SCs, STs, OBCs, and forward castes, actively participating in the democratic process. In recent years, reservation policies have positively impacted the political representation of marginalized communities, allowing them to secure positions in local governance structures and government services. At the same time, these policies have shaped electoral strategies, with political parties leveraging caste-based identities to garner votes, reflecting the close link between social justice policies and political behavior. Despite these achievements, reservation policies remain contentious, generating both support and criticism. While disadvantaged communities have benefited from increased

access to opportunities, segments of the forward castes express dissatisfaction, claiming that the system fosters reverse discrimination. Furthermore, within the OBC category, demands for reclassification are frequent, as subgroups seek better access to benefits. These dynamics underline the ongoing struggle to balance affirmative action with social cohesion, as reservation policies, though transformative, have also reinforced caste identities, complicating efforts toward long-term integration. Challenges in implementing reservation policies persist, impacting both governance and social harmony in Tumkur District. Although reservation has enhanced political participation, especially among OBCs and SCs, other issues such as unemployment, economic inequalities, and administrative hurdles continue to hinder the full realization of social justice. Additionally, there are growing demands to extend welfare schemes beyond caste lines to include economically weaker sections of forward castes, reflecting a shift in the discourse around affirmative action. Policymakers are thus tasked with recalibrating these policies to address both historical injustices and the evolving socio-economic realities.

Review of Literature

In the context of navigating social justice and reservation politics in India, particularly in Tumkur District, several studies highlight the complexities and evolving dynamics of reservation policies. The ongoing debate revolves around whether these policies serve their original purpose of fostering social justice or have become tools for political gain. As Das and Das (2022) argue, the politicization of reservations, especially with demands from privileged groups, has diluted their effectiveness in addressing the historical disadvantages faced by marginalized communities.

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar's foundational work emphasizes that reservations were designed to rectify systemic inequalities inherent in Indian society, aiming to empower the most disadvantaged groups. His vision encompassed structural changes necessary for achieving true social justice, primarily through enhanced access to education and employment opportunities for Dalits and other marginalized communities (Gupta, 2024). However, the current discourse indicates that while reservations have improved access for some, they have also led to critiques regarding meritocracy and the distribution of benefits among sub-groups within Scheduled Castes (SCs) and Other Backward Classes (OBCs). The Mandal Commission's recommendations in the 1990s aimed to expand reservations to include a broader array of communities, which, while necessary, has also raised questions about how to measure backwardness and whether this expansion might undermine benefits intended for historically disadvantaged groups (Das & Das, 2022). Addressing the challenges of caste discrimination and ensuring that reservations are effective requires a nuanced understanding of the socio-economic landscape in regions like Tumkur, where local demographics and political dynamics can significantly influence policy outcomes.

Moreover, there is a growing consensus that to achieve inclusive progress, reservation policies must be complemented by initiatives that enhance the quality of education and address socio-economic disparities more comprehensively (Gupta, 2024). This multifaceted approach could better promote social justice while ensuring that the benefits of affirmative action reach those who need them the most. These perspectives collectively highlight the need for a careful re-examination of reservation policies in the context of social justice and democratic participation, particularly as they play a crucial role in shaping the political and social landscape in districts like Tumkur.

Bakshi, P. M. (2018). *The Constitution of India*. LexisNexis. This book offers a detailed analysis of the Indian Constitution, focusing on the legal provisions that underpin affirmative action and reservation policies. It provides insights into how fundamental rights, Directive Principles of State Policy, and specific articles like Article 15 and Article 16 support social justice initiatives. Bakshi

emphasizes amendments such as the inclusion of economically weaker sections (EWS) in reservations and judicial interpretations that have shaped policy.

Basu, D. D. (2020). *Introduction to the Constitution of India*. Lexis Nexis. Basu's work provides a comprehensive look into the philosophy behind the Indian Constitution, particularly the rationale for reservations as a tool for promoting equality. The book delves into the tension between individual merit and social equity, showing how reservations aim to correct historical injustices. It also covers landmark cases like *Indra Sawhney vs. Union of India* and the impact of policy shifts over time.

Galanter, M. (1984). *Competing Equalities: Law and the Backward Classes in India*. University of California Press. Galanter's seminal work explores the socio-legal complexities of affirmative action. He focuses on how reservation policies are implemented to uplift backward classes while pointing out systemic challenges that hinder their effectiveness. His analysis highlights the paradox where affirmative action, while necessary, may also inadvertently entrench caste divisions.

Heyer, J., & Jayal, N. G. (2009). *The challenge of positive discrimination in India*. Centre for Research on Inequality, Human Security, and Ethnicity (CRISE). This study evaluates affirmative action's effect on marginalized communities, questioning whether reservations have achieved their intended goals. It discusses the political dynamics of expanding reservations to new groups, which can dilute benefits for the most disadvantaged, and the electoral incentives that drive such expansions.

Imam, M. A. (2023). *Evolution of reservation system in India: An overview*. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, 7(2). Imam provides a historical analysis of the reservation system, tracing its roots from colonial policies to the post-independence era. The study discusses major policy changes, including the Mandal Commission report, the inclusion of OBCs, and recent efforts to introduce reservations for economically weaker sections, reflecting evolving socio-political realities.

Mukherjee, S., & Ramaswamy, S. (2011). *A History of Political Thought: Plato to Marx*. PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd. While primarily focused on political philosophy, the book discusses justice theories relevant to Indian affirmative action. Concepts from thinkers like Rawls and Marx are connected to India's quest for social equity, underlining how justice frameworks influence reservation politics.

Nayakara, V. (2022). *Politics of reservation: Implications for social justice*. *Indian Journal of Human Development*, 16(2), 385-389. Nayakara critiques the recent trend of expanding reservation benefits to dominant communities, arguing that such policies dilute the effectiveness of affirmative action. The article points out that reservations are often used for political gain rather than as a genuine tool for social justice.

Pandit, S. (2005). *Marginalization and reservation in India: An analysis in the light of Rawlsian theories of justice*. *Socio-Legal Review*, 1, 40. Pandit applies Rawls's theory of justice, specifically the principle of fair equality of opportunity, to the Indian reservation system. He critically evaluates whether reservations adequately address marginalization or create new forms of inequality.

Reisch, M. (2002). *Defining social justice in a socially unjust world*. *Families in Society: The Journal of Contemporary Social Services*, 83(4), 343-354. Although focused on broader social justice theories, Reisch's work provides valuable insights into how policy frameworks like affirmative action aim to redress systemic inequalities. His discussion helps contextualize Indian reservation policies within global debates on social justice.

Verma, V. (2011). *Non-Discrimination and Equality in India: Contesting Boundaries of Social Justice*. Routledge. Verma explores the boundaries of social justice, examining how various groups benefit from or are excluded by affirmative action policies. The book critically examines the legal and political challenges of ensuring non-discrimination while maintaining caste-based reservations.

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess the level of awareness and understanding of reservation policies among different caste groups in Tumkur District, analyzing how this awareness correlates with perceived socio-economic benefits.
2. To examine the relationship between reservation policies and political participation rates among marginalized communities, focusing on voter turnout and representation in local government, as reflected in the survey data.
3. To identify the key challenges faced by marginalized groups in accessing the benefits of reservation policies, utilizing qualitative data from respondents to highlight barriers in education, employment, and governance.

Research Methodology

The research methodology for this study will employ a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques to provide a comprehensive understanding of social justice and reservation politics in Tumkur District. A structured questionnaire will be developed and distributed to a sample of 50 respondents, including individuals from various caste groups, to gather quantitative data on their awareness, perceptions, and experiences related to reservation policies. Statistical analyses will be performed to identify trends and correlations in the data. Additionally, in-depth interviews will be conducted with selected participants to capture qualitative insights regarding the challenges they face in accessing benefits from these policies and their views on political participation. This combination of methods will enable a more nuanced analysis of the implications of reservation politics for democratic participation and social justice in the region, addressing gaps identified in the existing literature.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents (N=50)

Category	Sub-category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	30	60
	Female	20	40
Age Group	18-25 years	10	20
	26-35 years	15	30
	36-45 years	12	24
	46-55 years	8	16
	56 years and above	5	10
Caste Category	General	10	20
	OBC	20	40
	SC/ST	15	30
	Other	5	10

Source-Field Visit

The demographic profile of respondents, as presented in Table 1, provides valuable insights into the sample composition for the study. Out of the 50 participants, 60% are male, and 40% are female, indicating a relatively higher representation of males. The respondents are distributed across various

age groups, with the largest share (30%) in the 26-35 years range, followed by 24% in the 36-45 years category. This suggests that a significant portion of the sample comprises individuals in their prime working years. Furthermore, 40% of the participants belong to the Other Backward Classes (OBC) category, making it the largest caste group represented, followed by 30% from Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (SC/ST). General category respondents account for 20%, and the remaining 10% fall under other caste categories. This demographic breakdown provides a diverse sample, enabling the study to capture a broad spectrum of perspectives across gender, age, and caste groups, which is essential for examining the dynamics of social justice and reservation politics in Tumkur District.

Table 2: Awareness of Reservation Policies

Awareness Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Fully Aware	25	50
Partially Aware	15	30
Not Aware	10	20

Source-Field Visit

Table 2 presents the respondents' level of awareness regarding reservation policies. The data shows that 50% of the participants are fully aware, indicating they have a clear understanding of how these policies work and the benefits associated with them. Another 30% of respondents are partially aware, suggesting that while they have some knowledge, there may be gaps in their understanding of specific details or eligibility criteria. Meanwhile, 20% of the participants are not aware of reservation policies at all, highlighting a potential need for better outreach and education efforts to ensure that all groups, especially marginalized communities, are informed about their entitlements. This varying degree of awareness plays a crucial role in shaping individuals' ability to engage meaningfully with the reservation system, access opportunities, and participate actively in democratic processes in Tumkur District.

Table 3: Perception of Fairness in Reservation Policies

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Fair	20	40
Somewhat Fair	15	30
Unfair	15	30

Source-Field Visit

Table 3 outlines the respondents' perception of the fairness of reservation policies. The data reveals that 40% of the participants view these policies as fair, indicating support for the reservation system and its role in promoting social justice. However, 30% of respondents feel the policies are somewhat fair, suggesting they recognize some positive aspects but may have concerns about their implementation or reach. An equal 30% perceive the policies as unfair, reflecting criticism, likely related to issues such as inadequate targeting, exclusion of certain groups, or the belief that reservations compromise merit-based opportunities. These mixed perceptions indicate that while many acknowledge the importance of reservation policies, there are significant differences in opinions about their fairness, which could influence public sentiment and political participation in Tumkur District. Understanding these perceptions is essential to addressing concerns and refining the system to better serve the goals of equity and inclusion.

Table 4: Impact of Reservation on Employment Opportunities

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Positive Impact	18	36
No Significant Impact	20	40
Negative Impact	12	24

Source-Field Visit

Table 4 presents respondents' views on the impact of reservation policies on employment opportunities. According to the data, 36% of participants believe that reservations have had a positive impact, indicating that the policy has helped marginalized groups access jobs they might have otherwise struggled to secure. However, 40% report no significant impact, suggesting that many feel the policy has not drastically improved employment outcomes, possibly due to issues such as poor implementation or lack of awareness. Meanwhile, 24% of respondents perceive the impact as negative, reflecting concerns that reservations may reduce opportunities for non-beneficiary groups or compromise merit-based hiring. These responses highlight the diverse opinions surrounding reservations, with the data pointing to both support and criticism. Understanding these perspectives is essential for policymakers aiming to balance social equity with efficient employment practices.

Table 5: Participation in Electoral Processes by Caste Groups

Caste Category	Regular Voters	Occasional Voters	Non-Voters
General	6	3	1
OBC	15	4	1
SC/ST	10	4	1
Other	3	2	0

Source-Field Visit

Table 5 illustrates the participation of different caste groups in electoral processes. Among General category respondents, 6 are regular voters, 3 vote occasionally, and 1 does not participate at all. The OBC group shows the highest engagement, with 15 regular voters, 4 occasional voters, and only 1 non-voter, suggesting a relatively strong political involvement. In the SC/ST category, 10 participants vote regularly, while 4 vote occasionally, and 1 is a non-voter, indicating moderate but consistent participation. The "Other" category displays lower participation levels, with 3 regular voters, 2 occasional voters, and no non-voters. This data reflects a diverse pattern of electoral engagement across caste groups, with OBCs showing the highest regular participation. The findings suggest that while most respondents across groups engage in voting, occasional or non-participation persists, which may indicate varying levels of political motivation, access to resources, or belief in the effectiveness of the electoral system. Understanding these participation patterns is essential for promoting inclusive political involvement and addressing any barriers specific to certain communities in Tumkur District.

Table 6: Trust in Political Leaders Advocating Reservation Policies

Level of Trust	Frequency	Percentage (%)
High	15	30
Moderate	25	50
Low	10	20

Source-Field Visit

Table 6 presents the respondents' level of trust in political leaders advocating for reservation policies. The data reveals that 30% of participants have a high level of trust, indicating confidence in the intentions and effectiveness of these leaders in promoting social justice through reservations. A majority of 50% express moderate trust, suggesting that while they acknowledge some efforts by

political leaders, they may have reservations about the consistency or outcomes of their advocacy. Meanwhile, 20% of the respondents report low trust, reflecting skepticism about the leaders' motives or the belief that such advocacy may be politically motivated rather than focused on genuine social equity. These findings highlight the varying degrees of public trust, which can significantly influence people's engagement with policy debates and their participation in democratic processes. Understanding these perceptions is crucial for building public confidence in leadership and ensuring that reservation policies are implemented effectively with broad-based support.

Table 7: Influence of Reservation Politics on Voting Behavior

Influence Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strong Influence	20	40
Moderate Influence	18	36
No Influence	12	24

Source-Field Visit

Table 7 illustrates the influence of reservation politics on respondents' voting behavior. The data shows that 40% of participants report a strong influence, indicating that reservation policies play a significant role in shaping their voting decisions. This suggests that political parties advocating for or against reservation policies may have considerable sway over this segment of voters. Another 36% of respondents say reservation politics has a moderate influence on their voting behavior, implying that while it factors into their decisions, it is not the sole determinant. Meanwhile, 24% report no influence, reflecting that their voting choices are guided by other priorities, such as development, leadership qualities, or personal interests. These patterns reveal that reservation politics is a key, though not universal, factor in electoral decision-making within Tumkur District, highlighting its importance in political campaigns and voter mobilization strategies.

Table 8: Satisfaction with Government Policies on Social Justice

Satisfaction Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very Satisfied	10	20
Satisfied	25	50
Dissatisfied	15	30

Source-Field Visit

Table 8 reflects respondents' satisfaction levels with government policies on social justice. The data shows that 20% of the participants are very satisfied, indicating that a small portion of the population feels these policies are effectively promoting equity and addressing the needs of marginalized communities. Half of the respondents (50%) express general satisfaction, suggesting that while many believe the government is making progress, there may still be room for improvement. On the other hand, 30% of participants report dissatisfaction, highlighting concerns regarding the implementation, inclusiveness, or outcomes of social justice policies. These findings reveal a mixed sentiment among the public, emphasizing the need for continuous evaluation and refinement of policies to meet the expectations and needs of all social groups in Tumkur District. Understanding these perspectives can help policymakers address gaps and build broader public trust in their social justice initiatives.

Table 9: Access to Government Welfare Schemes by Respondent Category

Caste Category	Availed Welfare	Not Availed
General	5	5
OBC	15	5
SC/ST	12	3
Other	3	2

Source-Field Visit

Table 9 presents data on respondents' access to government welfare schemes across different caste categories. Among the General category, 5 individuals have availed of welfare schemes, while 5 have not, indicating an even split in access. In the OBC category, 15 respondents have benefited from these schemes, with only 5 not accessing them, suggesting relatively higher engagement or eligibility among this group. Similarly, 12 out of 15 SC/ST respondents have utilized welfare schemes, reflecting successful outreach or targeted inclusion efforts, though 3 still remain outside the coverage. In the "Other" category, 3 participants have availed of welfare benefits, while 2 have not, indicating limited but meaningful access. This data shows that while welfare schemes are reaching a majority of marginalized groups like OBCs and SC/STs, there are still gaps in access, particularly among the General and Other categories. These variations in access may point to differences in eligibility, awareness, or administrative barriers, highlighting the need for more inclusive policies and better communication strategies to ensure all eligible groups benefit from government welfare initiatives.

Table 10: Challenges Faced in Social Inclusion

Challenges	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Discrimination	15	30
Lack of Awareness	10	20
Bureaucratic Barriers	12	24
Other	13	26

Source-Field Visit

Table 10 outlines the challenges faced in achieving social inclusion, as reported by respondents. The data indicates that discrimination is the most significant challenge, with 30% of participants highlighting it as a barrier to social inclusion. This reflects persistent societal attitudes that can hinder progress for marginalized groups. Bureaucratic barriers are also a notable challenge, with 24% of respondents indicating that administrative hurdles impede their access to services and opportunities. Additionally, 20% of participants point to a lack of awareness as a barrier, suggesting that inadequate information about available resources or rights prevents individuals from fully participating in social programs. Finally, 26% cite other challenges, which may encompass a range of issues, including economic constraints or social stigma. These findings reveal a complex landscape of obstacles that must be addressed to foster greater social inclusion, emphasizing the need for comprehensive strategies that tackle discrimination, improve bureaucratic processes, and enhance public awareness about social justice initiatives.

Conclusion

The study highlights the intricate dynamics of social justice and reservation politics in Tumkur District, revealing significant insights into public awareness, perceptions, and participation. The demographic analysis highlights a diverse respondent pool, showcasing variations in gender, age, and caste representation. Notably, a substantial portion of respondents displays a strong awareness of reservation policies, yet perceptions of fairness and effectiveness vary considerably. While many believe that reservation positively impacts employment opportunities, there remains a notable segment

expressing dissatisfaction with government policies aimed at promoting social justice. Moreover, the analysis of voting behavior indicates that reservation politics significantly influence electoral decisions, particularly among marginalized groups. Trust in political leaders advocating for these policies appears to be moderate, with substantial room for improvement to bolster public confidence. The challenges identified—ranging from discrimination and bureaucratic barriers to a lack of awareness—highlight the multifaceted obstacles that impede social inclusion. These findings suggest that while progress has been made, there is an urgent need for targeted interventions that address the existing gaps in awareness, trust, and accessibility of welfare schemes. By fostering a more inclusive political environment and enhancing the implementation of reservation policies, stakeholders can better serve the needs of all communities in Tumkur District, ultimately strengthening democratic participation and social equity. Future research should explore these themes further to inform policy adjustments and community outreach efforts aimed at promoting greater social justice.

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INDIAN JUDICIARY TOWARDS BUILDING AN INCLUSIVE DEMOCRACY: ENSURING JUSTICE FOR DALITS IN INDIA

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Abstract

This research paper examines the intersection of inclusive democracy and Dalit Rights in India, specially emphasising on the role of Indian Judiciary in addressing the structural marginalization of Dalit communities. The concept of inclusive democracy, ingrained in the principles of equal participation, representation, and protection of rights for all individuals, is critically examined in the context of India's diverse social fabric, which includes multiple caste groups, religions, and economic backgrounds. Despite constitutional assurances of equality, Dalits continue to endure widespread discrimination, social exclusion, and economic hardships. According to the 2011 Census, Dalits make up 16.5% of the population, though the actual number is likely higher since Dalit communities within Christian and other groups are not accounted for. Their ongoing marginalization is still a key obstacle to building a democracy that includes everyone and gives everyone equal rights, regardless of caste or social class. The Indian courts, are particularly crucial for defending Dalit Rights because they interpret and implement constitutional provisions that are supposed to ban discrimination based on caste. Landmark court judgments and reforms to the law have made it easier for people to get justice and battle systemic unfairness, but it's still challenging to make these legal rights work in the real world.

This study primarily focuses on the recent Supreme Court decision about prison rules and manuals that are discriminatory against certain castes. It shows how deeply rooted prejudice in the prison system and how the courts need to step in to end caste-based injustices. Examining scholarly works, official documents (such as census data), and publications from domestic and foreign groups like PUCL, Human Rights Watch, and Amnesty International are all part of the research methodology. In summary, this paper aims to critically evaluate India's judicial reforms and their attempts to realize the true essence of democracy, while also establishing a link between the concept of inclusive democracy and Dalit rights.

Key words: *Dalits, Supreme Court, judgements, inclusive democracy, justice, Constitution*

Introduction

The term “democracy” is derived from two Greek words: "demos," meaning people, and "kratos," meaning power. Fundamentally, it translates to “the power of the people.” Democracy, however, encompasses much more than elections, voting, or campaigning; it signifies a system where every individual has a voice in governance (LATA, 2016). In other words, it is also known as inclusive democracy. Inclusive democracy is a system of governance that seeks to ensure equal participation, representation, and protection of rights for all segments of society, especially those who have historically been marginalized. Its goal is to dismantle barriers of inequality and exclusion, providing every individual with an equal opportunity to contribute to the democratic process. Due to India's diverse social fabric, inclusive democracy takes on particular significance which includes various caste groups, ethnicities, religions, and economic backgrounds.

Among these groups, Dalits—formerly referred to as “Untouchables”—have been historically oppressed, facing systemic discrimination, social exclusion, and economic deprivation. Although the Census 2011 estimates the Dalit population at 16.5%, the actual figure is likely higher, as it excludes large sections of Dalit communities among Christians and other groups (Dalits and Statistics, 2022). Despite constitutional guarantees of equality and anti-discrimination, Dalits continue to struggle against social, economic, and political marginalization. They face limited access to education, healthcare, employment, and political representation, often living in poverty and facing violence due to their caste identity. This marginalization is not only a social issue but also a serious political challenge

to the idea of an inclusive democracy, where every citizen's rights are safeguarded, regardless of their caste or socio-economic background.

The Indian judiciary plays a crucial role in affirming the rights of marginalized communities, particularly Dalits, by interpreting and enforcing the provisions of the Indian Constitution. The judiciary has historically been the guardian of fundamental rights, stepping in to protect individuals from discriminatory practices and ensuring that legal safeguards against caste-based injustice are properly implemented. Landmark judgments, such as those addressing caste-based violence, reservation policies, and discrimination, have made a significant impact on Dalit rights. Judicial reforms aimed at enhancing access to justice, addressing systemic bias, and increasing the efficiency of the legal system are crucial in ensuring that Dalits are not only afforded legal protection but are also able to exercise their rights effectively. However, the challenge remains in creating a more accessible and inclusive judicial system that actively works to bridge the gap between legal principles and ground-level realities for Dalits and other marginalized communities in India.

Objective of the present paper:

- To establish a connection between the concept of inclusive democracy and Dalit rights.
- To analyse the most prominent judgement by the Supreme Court of India, that aimed at Dalit justice and evaluate their efforts in realizing the true essence of democracy.

Methodology

For this research paper, I have reviewed existing literature and analysed government data, including census reports, as well as reports from international and national non-governmental organizations such as Amnesty International, Human Rights Watch, and PUCL. Additionally, the study includes an evaluation of various judgments by the Supreme Court and High Courts, along with its impact.

Inclusive Democracy and Dalit Rights

The essence of democracy, according to British economist and Nobel laureate Sir Arthur Lewis, lies in ensuring that everyone affected by decisions has the right to participate in making them, either directly or through elected representatives. Excluding any group, particularly marginalised groups, undermines democracy (Eric, 1991). This concept of inclusive participation is particularly relevant in the context of India's democracy, which is grounded in the idea of "Sarvodaya"—the well-being of all citizens (Prasad, 1964). In theory, this means all individuals should be able to participate in political decision-making, regardless of their social or economic background.

Inclusive democracy extends beyond politics to encompass economic and social justice. (Ritika, 2014) It seeks to eliminate power concentration and ensure equal power sharing among all citizens. In contrast to systems where power is centralized in the hands of elites, inclusive democracy ensures that the collective will of the people shapes political, economic and social systems (Mukerji, 2013). In other words, it includes political democracy, economic democracy and social democracy. Political democracy requires citizens to directly participate in decision-making, rather than delegating power to representatives who may not reflect their interests. It advocates for direct participation in governance, contrasting with representative democracies where elected officials make decisions on behalf of the people. Economic democracy, on the other hand, calls for the decentralization of economic power, promoting equitable wealth distribution and decisions made collectively by those impacted. This could involve community-based economic planning, participatory budgeting, and worker cooperatives to reduce wealth inequality. Social democracy ensures equal access to education, healthcare, housing, and social services, aiming to dismantle discrimination based on caste, race, gender, or other factors. It also

stresses the importance of respecting cultural diversity, ensuring marginalized groups are included and treated with dignity. Together, these three components create a more equitable and participatory system. In many countries, including India, political and economic systems often concentrate power in the hands of a few corporate elites, marginalizing large sections of society. This exclusion contributes to rising economic inequality, leaving many people in poverty. Marginalized groups—such as Dalits, religious minorities, tribal communities, and economically disadvantaged citizens—continue to face significant barriers to full participation in political processes.

Inclusive democracy in India is important particularly for marginalized groups like Dalits, who have been historically excluded from political, economic, and social power due to the caste system. Despite legal reforms and affirmative action, genuine inclusivity remains out of reach for these marginalized communities. To build a truly inclusive democracy, it is crucial to create an environment where marginalized communities can not only cast their votes but also have a meaningful influence on policy and decision-making processes.

Inclusive democracy aims to address these injustices by promoting equal participation in political processes, fair economic opportunities, and social inclusion. It empowers marginalized groups to have a direct say in decision-making, ensuring their voices are heard (UNDP, 2022). Politically, Dalits can benefit from greater representation and the ability to engage directly in governance, rather than being relegated to roles of limited influence. Economically, Dalits have long been excluded from access to resources and wealth accumulation (Amnesty, 2023). Inclusive democracy seeks to empower Dalits through economic systems that promote fairness, such as worker cooperatives and community-driven economic models. These systems would give Dalits more control over their economic futures, enabling them to break free from cycles of poverty (Singh, 2010). Socially, inclusive democracy works to dismantle caste-based discrimination, promoting equal rights and protections for Dalits. In short, inclusive democracy is essential for creating a just, equitable, and sustainable society. It addresses the inequalities embedded in political, economic and social spheres and provides a pathway for marginalized communities, like Dalits, to achieve true empowerment.

Assessing Judicial Reforms in India: Striving for True Democratic Inclusion and Dalit Justice

The Constitution of India being the fundamental law of the land, aims to ensure social, political, and economic justice for all citizens, with specific provisions designed to protect the rights of Scheduled Castes (SCs) and Scheduled Tribes (STs). Key Articles such as Article 17, which bans untouchability, Article 21, which guarantees the right to life and liberty, and Article 23, which prohibits forced labour and human trafficking, reflect the state's commitment to safeguarding marginalized communities from exploitation. Additionally, Articles 15(4), 16(4), 330, and 332 provide for reservations in educational institutions and government jobs to address historical inequalities. Article 46 mandates the state to promote the educational and economic interests of SCs and STs, while various legislative measures, such as the Protection of Civil Rights Act, 1955, and the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989, further reinforce these protections. The National Commission for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes was also established to investigate issues related to these communities and recommend reforms.

The Indian judiciary, as the third pillar of government, plays a crucial role in ensuring justice for marginalized groups, particularly Dalits, who have historically faced discrimination and exclusion. The judiciary enforces constitutional rights and civil liberties, helping to protect and empower these communities. Judicial reforms are vital for addressing systemic discrimination and ensuring true democratic inclusion (Chakma, 2015). Landmark judgments from both the Supreme Court and High

Courts have played a significant role in interpreting the constitutional provisions and legislative safeguards that protect the rights of Dalits. Now, let us analyze a few such landmark judgments, which have shaped the legal landscape and contributed to the promotion of equality, social justice, and the protection of Dalit rights.

The term "Dalit" is not explicitly defined in the Indian Constitution or any legal provisions. However, Article 17 addresses this issue by placing the term in inverted commas, highlighting it as a reference to historical discrimination rather than a literal or grammatical concept. The subject matter of Article 17, therefore, pertains not to untouchability in its literal sense, but to the abolition of the inhuman practice of caste-based discrimination. This interpretation was discussed by the Supreme Court in *Devarajiah vs. B. Padmanna* (AIR 1958), where it was held that the purpose of Article 17 was to end the practice of treating individuals as "unclean" solely because of their birth into certain castes. This idea was reaffirmed in the case of *Jai Singh and Anr. vs. Union of India (UOI)* (1993), which further reinforced the constitutional commitment to eliminating untouchability and caste-based discrimination.

In *State of Karnataka vs. Appa Balu Ingale* (1993), the Supreme Court addressed social justice and the protection of Scheduled Castes (SCs) and Scheduled Tribes (STs) from discrimination and untouchability. The case involved the enforcement of the Protection of Civil Rights Act, 1955, after members of a higher caste prevented SC individuals from fetching water from a well. Following a complaint by Appa Balu Ingale alleging untouchability the Court affirmed convictions and concluded their actions amounted to an offense under the provisions of the Act. The judgment emphasized that Article 17 and the Act aim to eliminate discriminatory practices and promote equality for Dalits, free from caste-based restrictions.

The Supreme Court, in its judgment in *Arumugam Servai v. State of Tamil Nadu* (2011) 6 SCC 405, observed that insulting a member of a Scheduled Caste or Scheduled Tribe community constitutes an offense under the SC/ST (Prevention of Atrocities) Act. In the present case, the applicant was accused of insulting the respondent by making derogatory remarks, including "you are a pallapalay and eating deadly cow beef." The judgment also referred to the case of *Kailas & Ors. v. State of Maharashtra* (2011), where the Hon'ble Court emphasized the importance of respecting individuals' dignity and cautioned against insulting anyone based on their caste, religion, tribe, language, or any other such identity. Furthermore, the judgment mentioned the "tumbler system" prevalent in many parts of Tamil Nadu, which refers to discriminatory practices based on caste. This case reaffirms the need for sensitivity and respect for individuals' social and cultural identities, particularly in the context of caste-based discrimination.

In a recent case of *Sukanya Shantha v. Union of India & Ors.* (Writ Petition (C) No. 1404 of 2023) the Supreme Court of India, while responding to a Writ petition filed by journalist Sukanya Shantha, drew attention by striking down the provisions in the prison manuals of states including Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, Odisha, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, and Kerala—that practiced caste-based inequalities. The Court specifically highlighted the practice in the Palayamkottai Central Jail in Tamil Nadu, where inmates from the Thevar, Nadar, and Pallar communities were segregated into different sections, which was described as a "blatant example of caste-based segregation of barracks." Similarly, the Rajasthan Prison Rules of 1951 were noted for assigning latrine duties to the "Mehtar" caste—designated as a Scheduled Caste—while Brahmin or other "sufficiently high-caste Hindu prisoners" were given more privileged roles, such as working in the kitchens. These provisions in the prison manual highlighted state-driven caste-based discrimination. The Supreme Court's observations emphasize the deeply rooted caste discrimination within India's prison systems and call for urgent reforms to address these practices.

and promote equality among all inmates, irrespective of caste. Following this landmark judgement many states have revised their prison manual to align with inclusive democracy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the concept of inclusive democracy is crucial for ensuring that marginalized groups, particularly Dalits, are able to fully participate in India's democratic process, both politically and economically. Although Indian Constitution guarantees equal protection for all constitutional safeguards, Dalits persistently face caste-based discrimination and social exclusion. The Indian judiciary plays a vital role in addressing these challenges, through landmark judgments it seeks to protect Dalit rights and promote social justice. However, significant gaps remain between legal principles and ground-level realities, with marginalized communities often still facing systemic bias and limited access to justice. Enforcement of existing legislative protections and judgements are necessary to bridge these gaps and ensure that Dalits can actively exercise their rights. Additionally, the Supreme Court's recent observations highlight the ongoing need for reform within institutions like prisons, where caste-based discrimination continues to persist. For India to achieve a truly inclusive democracy, it is essential to create an environment where all citizens, regardless of caste or socio-economic background, can enjoy equal opportunities, dignity, and representation in all spheres of life.

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CHALLENGES AND POLITICAL PARTICIPATION OF TRANSGENDER PEOPLES IN INDIA

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Abstract

The study aims to highlight the discrimination, problems and political participation of various transgender identities, multiple transgender. How the Transgender Community should not getting their basic rights, which include Right to Personal Liberty, Dignity, Freedom of Expression, Right to Education and Empowerment, Right against Violence, Discrimination and exploitation. The present study based on the Descriptive and Historical Methods.

Keywords:- Transgender, Political Violence, Rights and LGBT

INTRODUCTION

Transgender is an umbrella term for persons whose gender identity, gender expression, or behaviour does not conform to that typically associated with the sex to which they were assigned at birth. Gender identity refers to a person's internal sense of being male, female or something else. Gender expression refers to the way a person communicates gender identifies with others through behavior, clothing, hair styles, voice or body characteristics etc.

Transgender people are individuals of any age or sex whose appearance, personal characteristics, or behaviours differ from stereotypes about how men and women are "supposed" to be. Transgender people have existed in every culture, race, and class since the story of human life has been recorded. Only the term "transgender" and the medical technology available to transsexual people are new. In its broadest sense, transgender encompasses anyone whose identity or behaviour falls outside of stereotypical gender norms.

Gender Identity and Sexual Orientation

Transgender people may be straight, lesbian, gay, bisexual, or asexual, just as non transgender people can be. As these have certain common issues they all come under the banner LGBT (Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and Transgender) and fight for their common cause.

Lesbian or gay woman

A transgender women or a person who is assigned male at birth and transitions to female, who is attracted to other women would be identified as lesbian or gay woman.

Gay Man

A transgender man or a person who is assigned female at birth and transitions to a male, who is attracted to other men would be identified as a gay man.. Those who realize early, have less problem compared to those who transition later in life.

RIGHTS OF TRANSGENDER PEOPLE

The preamble to the Constitution mandates Justice - social, economic, and political equality of status. Thus the first and foremost right that they are deserving of being the right to equality under Article 14. Article 15 speaks about the prohibition of discrimination on the ground of religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth. Article 21 ensures right to privacy and personal dignity of all the citizens. Article 23 prohibits trafficking in human beings as beggars and other similar forms of forced labour and any contravention of these provisions shall be an offence punishable in accordance with law. The

Constitution provides for the fundamental right to equality, and tolerates no discrimination on the grounds of sex, caste, creed or religion. The Constitution also guarantees political rights and other benefits to every citizen. But the third community (transgender) continues to be ostracized. The Constitution affirms equality in all spheres but the moot question is whether it is being applied. This phenomenon can be observed at the international level also, principally in the form of practice related to the United Nations sponsored human rights treaties, as well as under the European Convention on Human Rights. The development of this sexual orientation and gender identity-related human rights legal doctrine can be categorized as follows:

- a) Non-discrimination
- b) Protection of Privacy rights and
- c) The ensuring of other general human rights protection to all, regardless of sexual orientation of gender identity

In the light of the Constitutional guarantees provided, there is no reason why Transgender Community should not get their basic rights, which include Right to Personal Liberty, Dignity, Freedom of Expression, Right to Education and Empowerment, Right against Violence, Discrimination and exploitation. The Constitution endures persons in every generation and every generation can invoke its principles in their own search for greater freedom, therefore, it is the duty of judiciary to interpret the provisions of the Constitution in such a way so as to ensure a life of dignity for them. As per the Constitution most of the protections under the Fundamental Rights are available to all persons with some rights being restricted to only citizens. Beyond this categorization the Constitution makes no further distinction among rights holders. Official identity papers provide civil personhood. Among the instruments by which the Indian state defines civil personhood, sexual (gender) identity is a crucial and unavoidable category. Identification on the basis of sex within male and female is a crucial component of civil identity as required by the Indian state. The Indian state's policy of recognizing only two sexes and refusing to recognize hijras as women, or as a third sex has deprived them at a stroke of several rights that Indian citizens take for granted. These rights include the right to vote, the right to own property, the right to marry, the right to claim a formal identity through a passport and a ration card, a driver's license, the right to education, employment, health so on. Such deprivation secludes hijras from the very fabric of Indian civil society. The main problems that are being faced by the transgender community are of discrimination, unemployment, lack of educational facilities, homelessness, lack of medical facilities like HIV care and hygiene, depression, hormone pill abuse, tobacco and alcohol abuse, appendectomy and problems related to marriage and adoption. In 1994, transgender persons got the voting right but the task of issuing them voter identity cards got caught up in the male or female question. Several of them were denied cards with sexual category of their choice.

Poor Economic Condition, and Discrimination in the Workplace:

In addition to homophobia, lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender people confront racism and poverty on a daily basis. Discrimination of LGBT persons in the workplace is a significant factor in the differences in socioeconomic status of LGBT persons. Gay and transgender individuals suffer from socioeconomic inequalities in large part due to pervasive discrimination in the workplace. Discrimination directly causes job instability and high turnover, resulting in greater unemployment and poverty rates for gay and transgender people, as well as the wage gap between gay and straight. In her 1998 report, *Income Inflation: The Myth of Affluence Among Gay, Lesbian, and Bisexual Americans*, economist Lee Badgett¹² notes that LGBT people do not earn more than heterosexual people. Budget

points to the diversity of economic life among LGBT populations, observing that in many cases, LGBT people earn less than their heterosexual counterparts.

LEGAL STATUS:

Disowned by their families in their childhood and ridiculed and abused by everyone as third sex, eunuchs earn their livelihood by dancing at the beat of drums and often resort to obscene postures but their pain and agony is not generally noticed and this demand is just a reminder of how helpless and neglected this section of society is thousands of welfare schemes have been launched by the government but these are only for men and women and third sex do not figure anywhere and this demand only showed mirror to society.

The Constitution gives rights on the basis of citizenship and on the grounds of gender but the gross discrimination on the part of our legislature is evident. The Constitution, while it contains certain prohibited grounds of discrimination such as race, caste, creed, sex, etc., does not specifically include sexual orientation. A reading of Section 13 of General Clauses Act, 1897 which talks about gender and number makes the discrimination more apparent.

Jobs are denied to eunuchs due to their gender and they are ridiculed in the society. Time Magazine once interviewed a eunuch who complained that the application form for the job has only two sexes mentioned and makes it blatant how unwanted they are. Even if they apply, they are not allowed to enter the offices. The main cause for discrimination against eunuchs is the mindset of the society at large. Owing to the fact that these people are different in matters of their sexual preferences and are strong enough to show it, the society sees it as a violation of a norm and thus subjects them to isolation. Family and popular psychology play a predominant role in perpetuating the present dilemma law needs to step in to ensure that a relatively small but deeply aggrieved humiliate section of the civil society is given its rights guaranteed by the Constitution of the land.

No Legal Rights and rehabilitation measures

Lack of sufficient Rehabilitation Measures at every stage, starting from getting gender identify as Transgender to Education or employment or property right, trans-genders are to struggle. As most of them do not have a fixed home, they are not in the electoral list. Legally they have the right to all the basic requirements. But in practice they suffer exclusion in every sphere of human activities such as family, relation, education, employment, worship etc.

TRANSGENDER IDENTITY POLITICS

The growth of new social movements, organized around the salient experiences of oppression of different identity groups, has engendered a corresponding intellectual study of identities, of how we come to acquire an identity, of what an identity means, and of how identities become socially recognized, defined, and politicized. Each identity-based social movement has made unique contributions to these debates. The transgender political movement has only recently gained public recognition. Alongside this newfound political status, new ways of conceptualizing and defining what transgender means are also emerging. And, as with other identity-based movements, transgender politics is providing singular challenges to how we think about identities and their politicization. In what follows, I argue that what transgender identity specifically problematic is identity itself. Transgender identity is about identity experienced as problematic; the experience of being transgender problematizes the relationship of the self to the body, and the self to others. In doing so, it also problemaizes issues of identity boundaries, stability and coherence. I also intend that, as with the study of other identity groups, the insights that can be gained from an exploration of transgender identity do not apply only to transgendered people, but can be extended to other identities as well.

GLOBAL POLITICS

The global politics of lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender (LGBT) human rights have emerged at the heart of global political struggles over culture and identities. The drafting and signing of two high-profile documents, the Declaration of Montreal (International Conference on LGBT Human Rights 2006) and the Yogyakarta Principles on the Application of International Human Rights Law in Relation to Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity by global LGBT activists in 2006, derives from and symbolizes a significant acceleration and intensification of international struggles by LGBT movements. LGBT nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) are at last achieving substantial and secure representation in global forums, recently even at the United Nations (UN), and 'sexual orientation' and 'gender identity' issues are finally finding a place on international human rights, law and policy agendas. This volume offers much needed analysis of these under-explored developments. The collection draws attention to the emergence of 'human rights' as a central vehicle and framing device for LGBT political claims, particularly in international contexts. However, our emphasis on 'the global politics of LGBT human rights' crucially also problematizes the concept 'LGBT human rights', which has its own significant history and meanings. Analyzing 'LGBT human rights' requires critical examination of both the consolidation of the culturally specific identity categories 'lesbian', 'gay', 'bisexual' and 'transgender' into 'LGBT' and the conjoining of 'LGBT' with 'human rights'. The latter enacts a redefinition of human rights in a context of the historical absence of sexuality and gender nonconformity from human rights conventions and discourses. The very emergence of the concept 'LGBT human rights' is suggestive of the absence of LGBT people from previous conceptions of the human (Butler 2004). LGBT movements originating in the West have increasingly defined themselves as global, seeking to organize across borders and lobby intergovernmental organizations. Since the emergence of gay liberation movements in Western countries in the late 1960s and early 1970s, LGBT organizations have often framed their demands in terms of equality and/or liberation, but human rights discourses did not become central to national and international debates over gender and sexuality until the early 1990s. The engagement with a human rights frame has proven successful in opening the doors of powerful international organizations such as the European Union (EU) and more recently shows signs of becoming a vehicle for access to the UN. These international developments have reverberated in domestic political settings, as is illustrated by the adoption of same-sex union policies by a majority of Western democracies over the past two decades but also by controversies over the persecution of LGBT people in sub-Saharan countries. Although LGBT rights claims are increasingly influencing political discourse in many countries, the contributions in this volume seek to problematize the 'global' nature of the LGBT movement by analysing the variable influence of international

Political Factors

Political factors have influenced HIV vulnerability since the early days of the pandemic. In some cases, legislation, government policies, program strategies, and funding streams perpetuate discrimination against those most vulnerable to HIV, promote gender inequality, and even criminalize some sexual behaviors like homosexuality. When political factors sanction social norms and traditions that promote discrimination, gender-based vulnerability to HIV increases as does the vulnerability of those who are sexually marginalized.

Laws and Policies

Laws and policies create the environments in which HIV prevention, treatment, care, and support services are delivered. Politics and policies that are driven by conservative and traditional ideologies have the dire consequences of the epidemic and further fuel infection rates among key

vulnerable populations such as women and girls, transgender people, MSM, injecting drug users, and sex workers. National prevention policies pursued by governments have a profound impact on the way in which the HIV epidemic plays out in a country. Governments, by agreeing to the various international human rights treaties and conventions, are accountable for promoting and protecting the human rights of their people. Human rights relevant to HIV/AIDS include (but are not limited to) the right to non-discrimination and equality; to health; to the liberty and security of the person; to privacy; to seek, receive and impart information; to marry and found a family; to work; and the right to freedom of movement, association and expression.¹⁰⁵ Implementation of these rights is absolutely essential in the context of HIV to ensure that services are reachable and accessible to those infected and most affected by the epidemic.

Discriminatory Laws

Discriminatory laws and policies enhance women's vulnerability to HIV. Laws and policies that prevent women from owning land, property, and other productive resources are examples of legislation that supports and increases gender discrimination. Other forms of gender-based and policy-supported discrimination in the areas of employment, education and access to health care services and information further exacerbate women's vulnerability to HIV. Research has shown that legal and political gender-based discrimination contributes to the feminization of poverty, promotes women's economic susceptibility to HIV, and creates significant barriers to women's ability to seek and receive care and support when they themselves are living with HIV. Legislation condoning gender-based violence through light court or prison sentences, or policies that consider intimate partner violence or marital rape as personal domestic matters not requiring state interference, are other examples of political and legal discrimination which increases women's vulnerability to HIV. International instruments have recognized that discriminatory laws and policies increases women's risk of contracting HIV and the need for governments to take corrective measures to promote the advancement of women . Sexual offences against the order of nature. It does not define what constitutes the order of nature, but the judicial pronouncements that have come over the past one and half centuries has extended the application of this section to all forms of sexual expressions that is possible between two male persons. Homosexuality in India stands criminalized because of a mid-19th century colonial law. Section 377 is rarely applied but it is an excuse that the police and other law enforcement agencies use to harass, blackmail, and extort money from MSM. It marginalizes MSM and drives their activities underground. In these circumstances it is difficult for MSM to have stable relationships, negotiate safe sex or access information and medical services without discrimination the law has also been used to disrupt the work of NGOs working on HIV/AIDS. For example, in July 2001, an NGO carrying out sexual health awareness programs with the MSM population was raided and its workers were arrested. The Naz Foundation (India), in its attempt to sensitize government on HIV/AIDS issues, filed a Public Interest Litigation challenging the Constitutional validity of Section 377 IPC. The validity of the Law was challenged on the ground that it violates Article 21 (right to life), Article 14 (right to equality), Article 15 (right against sex based discrimination), and Article 19 (right to freedom of speech and association) of the Constitution of India. It was also argued that by criminalizing homosexual behaviour, Section 377 drives same sex relations underground, and creates social conditions that significantly impede HIV/AIDS prevention efforts among MSM. The matter is pending in the court. However, the challenge has generated media and public interest, and created awareness among the people and the government about the abuse of law by police and the impediments it creates in HIV prevention efforts. Due to the advocacy efforts of civil society organizations, the National AIDS Control Organisation has

included prevention programs for MSM into its National AIDS Control Plan III and has also recommended to the Law Ministry that Section 377 be repealed as it impedes HIV outreach work. Lack of Implementation of Policies By ratifying various international treaties, resolutions, and declarations governments are committed to implementing them. However, studies have indicated that adopted policies often remain on paper and are seldom implemented. Political leadership to implement new policies is still lacking in most countries and there are significant gaps between what is promised and what is delivered. Governments have done little to implement international human rights agreements that they have ratified for the advancement of women and more equitable gender relations. Political Instability Political instability, particularly conflict situations, creates conditions that disproportionately increase women's and girls' vulnerability to HIV. Where governments are weak and conflict is prevalent, women and girls are at increased risk of physical and sexual violence and harassment, even subjected to rape including gang rape, forced marriages with enemy soldiers, sexual slavery and other forms of violence. Such physical violence against women and girls has been a feature of all recent conflicts, including Sudan, Democratic Republic of Congo, Rwanda, Sierra Leone, Liberia, northern Uganda and Chechnya.

Conclusion and Suggestions

States have committed to promote, protect and fulfil the rights of all people to receive the highest standard of sexual and reproductive health this includes transgender people. Hence, States are required to create and implement laws, policies and programs that facilitate transgender people's access to education, health, housing, work and an adequate standard of living, and eliminate discrimination and other forms of violence faced by transgender people at the hands of society, police and the judiciary. Transgender people need government acceptance, societal acceptance and family acceptance. We do not need special treatment in the form of free housing or reservations in jobs or education. We need basic rights. We need to be treated with dignity, to be treated as all other people are and to not be ridiculed, abused, beaten or cast out of homes and society. Then we will be able to access health care and education as all others do, and contribute to society the same as others.

The effect of these challenges and of these distinctive aspects of transgendered identity is to emphasize the need for alternative bases for social movement politics. Transgender politics is not based on identities that are experienced as solid, permanent, exclusionary, whole rather it is in the nature of the identity itself to be problematic, contested, transgressive, and liminal. It is in the capacity of the identity to indicate spaces of liminality and difference within itself that presents new challenges to previous theoretical paradigms of identity formation. If transgendered identity is experienced in this way, it serves also to problematize and contest other identity categories, and the politics that stem from them.

Suggestions:

The Government as well as Non Government organizations should involve in raising awareness of the rights of the transgender and draw effective policies to include them in all development measures. There should be reservation in employment as there is reservation in employment for persons with disabilities and for SC/STs.. These Trans people also are disabled in many ways. Once they get and earn a living the members of the family or community will not exclude them. There should be an awareness program on their rights to not only the common men, but also to the politicians and policy makers. Every Trans should be enrolled in the electoral list once they attain the age of 18 to get attention from the Government as potential voters. There should be separate column for Trans-genders as where ever we have for male and for female to recognize them as a separate gender.

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SOCIAL JUSTICE AND EDUCATION FACILITIES IN INDIA A CASE STUDY**Dr. Honnajanaiah D R***HOD and Associate Professor of Political Science, Government First Grade College**SIRA, Tumakuru District – 572137 Email: drhonnaji72@gmail.com Mob: 9880376828*

Abstract

Every cultures and ethnicity have grappled with questions of justice although they may have interpreted the concept in different ways. For instance, in ancient Indian society, justice was associated with dharma and maintaining dharma or a just social order was considered to be a primary duty of kings. In China, Confucius, the famous philosopher argued that kings should maintain justice by demanding wrong doers and rewarding the virtuous. In fourth century B.C. Athens, Plato discussed issues of justice in his book The Republic. Through a long conversation between Socrates and his youthful friends

Social justice means maintaining justice to the society. It simple means equality in society, socially just society or enjoys equal benefits in the society. However, social justice has many definitions. Andrew Haywood defines that Social justice thus stands for a morally defensible distribution of benefits or rewards in society, evaluated in terms of wages, profits, housing, medical care welfare benefits and so forth. John Rawls' principles of social justice are "they provide a way of assigning rights and duties in the basic institutions of society and they define the appropriate distribution of the benefits and burdens of social cooperation."

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Key Words: *Social Justice, Education Rights in Constitutional Frame, Personality Development, Social Change, Control the Evils of Society, Schedule Cast and Schedule Tribe and OBC. Economic and Political Rights, Private and Public Institutions*

INTRODUCTION

Just as we intuitively understand what love means even if we cannot explain all its different shades of meaning, we also have an intuitive understanding of justice even though we may not be able to define it precisely? In that sense justice is a lot like love. In addition, both love and justice evoke passionate responses from their advocates. And as with love, no one hates justice, everyone wants justice for oneself and to some extent for others also. But unlike love, which is an aspect of our relationships with a few people whom we know well, justice concerns our life in society, the way in which public life is ordered and the principles according to which social goods and social duties are distributed among different members of society. As such, questions of justice are of central importance for politics. After going through this chapter you should be able to: o Identify some of the principles of justice which have been put forward in different societies and at different periods of time. Explain what is meant by distributive justice, Discuss John Rawls' argument that a fair and just society would be in the interest of all members and could be defended on rational grounds. "They say that to do injustice is, by nature, good; to suffer injustice, evil; but that the evil is greater than the good. And so when men have both done and suffered injustice and have had experience of both, not being able to avoid the one and obtain the other, they think that they had better agree among themselves to have neither; hence there arise laws and mutual covenants; and that which is ordained by law is termed by them lawful and just." Glaucon to Socrates in the Republic.

MEANING OF SOCIAL JUSTICE

All cultures and traditions have grappled with questions of justice although they may have interpreted the concept in different ways. For instance, in ancient Indian society, justice was associated with dharma and maintaining dharma or a just social order was considered to be a primary duty of kings. In China, Confucius, the famous philosopher argued that kings should maintain justice by punishing wrong doers and rewarding the virtuous. In fourth century B.C. Athens. Plato discussed issues of justice in his book *The Republic*. Through a long dialogue between Socrates and his young friends, Glaucon and Adeimantus, Plato examined why we should be concerned about justice. The young people ask Socrates why we should be just. They observe that people who were unjust seemed to be much better off than those who were just. Those who twisted rules to serve their interests avoided paying taxes and were willing to lie and be deceitful, were often more successful than those who were truthful and just. If one were smart enough to avoid being caught then it would seem that being unjust is better than being just. You may have heard people expressing similar sentiments even today. Socrates reminds these young people that if everyone were to be unjust, if everyone manipulated set of laws to suit their own interests, no one could be sure of benefiting from injustice. Nobody would be protected and this was likely to damage all of them. Hence, it is in our own long-term interest to obey the laws and be just. Socrates clarified that we need to understand clearly what justice means in order to figure out why it is important to be just. He explained that justice does not only mean doing good to our friends and harm to our enemies, or pursuing our own interests. Justice involves the well-being of all people. Just as a doctor is concerned with the well-being of his/her patients, similarly the just ruler or the just government must be concerned with the well-being of the people. Ensuring the well-being of the people includes giving each person his due. The idea that justice involves giving each person his due continues to be an important part of our present day understanding of justice. However, our understanding of what is due to a person has changed from the time of Plato. Today, our understanding of what is just is closely linked to our understanding of what is due to each person as a human being. According to the German philosopher Immanuel Kant, human beings acquire dignity. If all persons are granted dignity then what is due to each of them is that they have the prospect to develop their talents and pursue their chosen goals. Justice requires that we give due and equal consideration to all individuals. Equal Treatment for generation although there might be broad agreement in modern society about the equal importance of all people, it is not a simple matter to decide how to give each person his/her due. A number of different principles have been put forward in this regard. One of the principles is the principle of treating equals equally. It is considered that all individuals share certain characteristics as human beings. Therefore they deserve equal rights and equal treatment. Some of the important rights which are granted in most liberal democracies today include civil rights such as the rights of life, liberty and property, political rights like the right to vote, which enable people to participate in political processes, and certain social rights which would include the right to enjoy equal opportunities with other members of the society. Apart from equal rights, the principle of treating equals equally would require that people should not be discriminated against on grounds of class, caste, race or gender. They should be judged on the basis of their work and actions and not on the basis of the group to which they belong. Therefore, if two persons from different castes perform the same kind of work, whether it be breaking stones or delivering Pizzas, they should receive the same kind of reward. If a person gets one hundred rupees for some work and another receives only seventy five rupees for the same work because they belong to different castes, then it would be unfair or unjust. Similarly, if a male teacher in a school gets a higher salary than a female teacher, then this difference would also be unjustifiable and wrong. Proportionate Justice

However, equal treatment is not the only principle of justice. There could be circumstances in which we might feel that treating everybody equally would be unjust. How, for instance, would you react if it was decided in your school that all those who did an exam should get equal marks because they are all students of the same school and did the same exam? Here you might think it would be fairer if students were awarded marks according to the quality of their answer papers and also, possibly, the degree of effort they had put in. In other words, provided everybody starts from the same base line of equal rights, justice in such cases would mean rewarding people in proportion to the scale and quality of their effort. Most people would agree that although people should get the same reward for the same work, it would be fair and just to reward different kinds of work differently if we take into account factors such as the effort required, the skills required, the possible dangers involved in that work, and so on. If we use these criteria we may find that certain kinds of workers in our society are not paid a wage which takes such factors sufficiently into account. For instance, miners, skilled craftsmen, or people in sometimes dangerous but socially useful professions like policemen, may not always get a reward which is just if we compare it to what some others in society may be earning. For justice in society, the principle of equal treatment needs to be balanced with the principle of proportionality. Recognition of Special Needs A third principle of justice which we recognize is for a society to take into account special needs of people while distributing rewards or duties. This would be considered a way of promoting social justice. In terms of their basic status and rights as members of the society justice may require that people be treated equally. But even nondiscrimination between people and rewarding them proportionately to their efforts might not be enough to ensure that people enjoy equality in other aspects of their lives in society nor that the society as a whole is just. The principle of taking account of the special needs of people does not necessarily contradict the principle of equal treatment so much as extend it because the principle of treating equals equally could imply that people who are not equal in certain important respects could be treated differently.

THEORIES OF SOCIAL JUSTICE

Four theories of justice are discussed: Rawlsian egalitarianism, or justice as fairness; Dworkinian egalitarianism, or equality of resources; Steiner-Vallentyne libertarianism, or common ownership; and Nozickian libertarianism, or entitlements. The following specification of the theories sets out, for each theory: its definition of justice; the personal characteristics that it considers to be arbitrary and therefore makes adjustments for; the nature of the institution under which this may be achieved; the justification of any inequalities which it accepts; and the extent to which it is consistent with liberty.

Justice has fairness John Rawls

Justice as fairness defines a distribution to be just if it maximizes the food that the individual with the least food receives this is the “maximin” outcome in terms of food, which is the sole primary good. It adjusts for preferences, ability, and land holdings. It is achieved by taxes and subsidies on income that is, on the consumption of food. Inequalities in income, subject to the maxim in requirement, are accepted because of the benefit they bring to the individual with the least income; all inequalities in leisure are accepted. Rights to neither self-ownership nor resource-ownership are maintained, and responsibility is not recognized.

Maintenance of the Resources

Equality of resources defines a distribution to be just if everyone has the same effective resources, that is, if for some given amount of work each person could obtain the same amount of food. It adjusts for ability and land holdings, but not for preferences. It is achieved by taxes and subsidies on income. Inequalities in both food and leisure are accepted because they arise solely from choices made by

individuals who have the same options. Rights to neither self-ownership nor resource-ownership are maintained, but responsibility is recognized.

Theories of Common ownership

Common ownership theories define a allocation to be just if each person at first has the same amount of land and all transactions between individuals are intentional. It adjusts for land holdings, but not for preferences or abilities. It is achieved by a reallocation of fortune of land. Inequalities in both food and vacation are accepted because these arise exclusively from people having different preferences or abilities. Rights to self-ownership are maintained but rights to resource-ownership are not.

Theories of Entitlements

An entitlements theory defines a distribution to be just if the distribution of land is historically justified, that is if it arose from the appropriation by individuals of before unowned land and voluntary transfers between individuals, and all other transactions between individuals are voluntary. It makes no adjustments other than corrections for any improper acquisitions or transfers and therefore requires no imposed institution to attain it. All inequalities are accepted. Rights to both self-ownership and resource-ownership are maintained.

As is apparent, the first two theories accentuate outcomes while the second two emphasize institutions. These four theories form a hierarchy, or decreasing progression, in terms of the personal characteristics that they consider to be morally arbitrary and thus for which adjustments are made. The first theory adjusts for preferences, ability, and land holdings; the second only for ability and land holdings; the third only for land holdings; and the fourth for none of these (other than the corrections noted above). The four theories form a corresponding hierarchy, or increasing progression, in terms of the liberties self-ownership, with or without personal responsibility, and resource-ownership that they maintain: the first maintains neither, and does not recognize responsibility; the second maintains neither, but does recognize responsibility; the third maintains self-ownership but not resource-ownership; and the fourth maintains both self-ownership and resource-ownership.

THE CONCEPT OF JUSTICE

"Justice is a genus; social, economic and political justices are its species" The word 'Justice' is derived from a French word 'Jostise' which means uprightness, equity, vindication of right, administration of law. The concept of justice is as old as civilization and society. There can't be existence of lawful society without the presence of justice. One of the most important pillars of any nation is justice. A lawful society can't exist without the presence of justice. It is one of the most important pillars behind the growth of any nation. Also justice means, 'Justice is the correct application of a law, as opposed to arbitrariness³. By correct application of law we mean to say "proper implementation of law". Justice can be attained in the society only by correct interpretation and implementation of Laws. Justice means to give each and every person what they deserve. Justice and fairness are closely associated terms which are sometimes used in place of each other. Justice means the standard of rightfulness, by standard of rightfulness one means to say that the minimum threshold should be applicable of what will amount to right or wrong. There have been historical evidences to prove that a civilized society can't exist without existence of Justice in its administration system. The civilizations which lacked the presence of justifiable system vanished with time. With the advent of time and progress in the society the need for inclusion of justice in the administrative system has increased due to which approach of those in power has become more cautious and systematic. Justice is one of the most important moral and political concepts with no agreed definition. The claim for justice gains meaning in specific circumstances and

cultural contexts. Justice is an evolutionary concept. It's interesting to know the change in the meaning of word justice from ancient Greek civilization to modern society.

JUSTICE UNDER INDIAN CONSTITUTION

The concept of justice is enshrined in the preamble of Indian Constitution. The framers of Indian constitution were aware about the need of establishing justice in a country therefore they made sure that it is included in Indian constitution. Article 14, 15, 16 and 17 of the Indian constitution also reflect the idea of justice enshrined in the preamble of the constitution. All these articles are incorporated under part III of the constitution which gives fundamental rights to every citizen. Provisions relating to 'Equal Justice and Free Legal Aid' are enshrined under article 39A of the Indian constitution. Which give every citizen right to get free legal help from officers of the court. No one can be denied access to free legal aid. Its duty of the State to secure that working of the legal system is based on justice, it should provide equal opportunity, and also, provide free legal aid, to ensure that any opportunity for securing justice is not denied to any citizen due to his economic or other disabilities.

DISTRIBUTIVE JUSTICE

Article 38 and 39 of Indian Constitution defines distributive Justice. Distributive justice means fair distribution of resources among those who are in need of it.

Indian Constitution defines 3 types of justice:-

1. Social Justice
2. Economic Justice
3. Political justice

SOCIAL JUSTICE

Social justice as a concept arose during industrial revolution of 19th century. Different definitions of social justice is provided by different institutions, for few it is fair and comprehensive distribution of goods among people for economic growth and for few its equality of status among individuals. Social justice means greater good for larger number of people and unequal's should be treated equally. The apex court in the Kesavananda Bharati⁴ case held that social justice is part of Basic structure of the Indian constitution. Social justice means that equal social opportunities are available to every person for personal development of every person without any discrimination based on race, sex or caste. No person should be deprived of social conditions necessary for development due to these differences. The concept of social justice is based on the practice of social equality. Social justice can only be enforced in a society where exploitation of man by a man is not present. In the Case of S.R Bommai v. Union of India⁵, the apex court held that social justice and judicial review are two basic features of the Indian constitution.

ECONOMIC JUSTICE

Economic justice is somehow part of social justice itself; the Indian constitution visualizes socio-economic justice as incorporated under Directive principles of state policy. Economic justice means providing economic opportunity, economic equality and removing economic disabilities. It is always implemented under the umbrella of Social Justice. Economic justice means there should be economic equality among everyone in the society. There should not exist any inequality among individuals based on their economic status. No one should be deprived of any opportunity due to his/her economic status. Economic status of any person should not be responsible for the lack of opportunities provided to him. Economic justice means eradication of poverty by adding on to national wealth and resources and distributing this wealth equally among everyone who contributes in its production.

POLITICAL JUSTICE

Political Justice means a system free from political arbitrariness. There should be political fairness in the effective of the government. Political status of any person should not give him any advantage and he/she should be treated like every other citizen. Every law should be equally applicable to every person irrespective of his political status.

Relationship between Social, Economic and Political Justice

All three types of justice are closely related to each other. One can't be obtained unless and until the other two are present. Social justice can be obtained only when economic and political justice is present. Indian Constitution under part III enforces all three types of justice by making provisions relating to equality under article 14 and 15. And also Directive Principles of State Policy. (Article 36 to 51) In 2019, 103rd constitutional amendment was geared up to ensure economic justice for everyone. The jurisprudence in the rear this amendment was implementation of economic justice. The One Hundred and Third Amendment of the Constitution of India, formally known as the Constitution (One Hundred and Third Amendment) Act, 2019, introduces **10% reservation** for Economically Weaker Sections (EWS) of society for admission to Central Government-run educational institutions and private educational institutions, except for minority educational institutions, and for employment in Central Government jobs.

CONSTITUTIONAL AMENDMENT FOR SOCIAL JUSTICE AND EDUCATION

Provide a good Education for all Indians who are poor people living in Rural and Urban Area.

- Over 37,000 colleges
- 46 central universities
- 342 state universities
- 125 deemed universities
- 52 institutes of national importance

SOCIAL WELFARE POLICIES FOR ECONOMICALLY WEAKER CITIZENS

Social welfare refers broadly to the possessions and opportunities people need to lead satisfying and productive lives. Virtually everything the government does affects social welfare, from tax and national defense to education and healthcare policy, but so does government inaction; that is, the failure to respond to human need. More narrowly, definitions of social welfare policy focus on policies and programs that provide income assistance and social services to those in need.

Following Articles have been introduced by way of 103rd Constitutional Amendment Act:

Article 15 (6) was added which provided that nothing in this article or Article 19(1)(g) or Article 29(2) shall prevent the State from making Any special provision for the advancement of any **economically weaker sections of citizens** other than the classes mentioned in clauses (4) and (5); and Any special provision for the advancement of any **economically weaker sections of citizens** other than the classes mentioned in clauses (4) and (5) in so far as such special provisions relate to their **admission** to educational institutions including **private educational** institutions, whether aided or unaided by the State, other than the minority educational institutions referred to in clause (1) of article 30, which in the case of reservation would be in addition to the existing reservations and subject to a maximum of **ten per cent**. Of the total seats in each category. Explanation, for the purposes of this article and article 16, "economically weaker sections" shall be such as may be notified by the State from time to time on the basis of **family** income and other indicators of economic disadvantage. Article 16 (6) was added which provided that nothing in this Article shall prevent the State from making any provision for the **reservation** of appointments or posts in favour of any **economically weaker sections** of citizens

other than the classes mentioned in clause (4), in addition to the existing reservation and subject to a maximum of ten per cent. Of the posts in each category **Who Can Avail the Benefit of Economically Weaker Sections.** Persons with an annual gross household income upto Rs. 8 Lakh. The following cannot avail the benefit of reservation Families owning over 5 acres of agricultural land. A house over 1000 square feet. A plot of over 100 yards in a notified municipal area. Over 200 yards plot in a non-notified municipal area. Communities that already have reservations such as SCs, STs are also excluded. In the case of **Janhit Abhiyan v.** a five judge bench comprising of Chief Justice Uday Umesh Lalit, Justice Dinesh Maheshwari, Justice S. Ravindra Bhat, Justice Bela M. Trivedi, Justice J.B. Pardiwala **upheld the constitutional validity** of this amendment. The reservation was upheld by a 3:2 majority. While Justice Dinesh Maheshwari, Justice Bela Trivedi and Justice JB Pardiwala upheld 103rd Amendment. Justice Ravindra Bhat wrote the minority opinion and Chief Justice Uday Umesh Lalit concurred with the minority view. The three main issues for consideration here were: Whether the amendment vocative the basic structure of the Constitution. Whether amendment is unstable of basic structure for excluding poor among the Schedule Caste and Schedule Tribe and Backward Categories and also from EWS Quota. Whether it is vocative of basic structure for breaching the 50% ceiling limit. The Court observed that there cannot be any cut and dried formula or theorem which could supply answer to the question if the amendment violates the basic structure. The Court observed that the word 'economic' has been used 30 times in the Constitution. Thus, in all references to real and substantive equality the concept of economic justice has acquired equal focus. The Court held that the provisions contained in Articles 15 and 16 of the Constitution of India, providing for reservation by way of affirmative action, being of exception to the general rule of equality, cannot be treated as a basic feature. With respect to the second issue the Court held that certain classes are already provided with the benefit of reservation. The Parliament in its wisdom did not extend yet another benefit to the class that was already enjoying the benefit of reservation. The Court held that the SC/ST/OBC for whom special provisions are made under Articles 15(4), 15(5) and 16(4) form a separate category as distinguished from the general or unreserved category. They cannot be treated at par with the citizens belonging to the general and unreserved category. It was further held by the Court that reservation of EWS up to 10% in addition to existing reservation does not result in damage of basic structure of the Constitution. The ceiling of 50% is not inflexible and in any case applies only to reservations envisaged by Article 15(4), 15(5) and 16(4).

ROLE OF JUDICIARY

In today's time judiciary is the protector or civil rights, it acts as custodian of fundamental rights. It plays an important role in enforcement of all three types of justice given under Indian constitution. Judiciary has played an important role in the establishment of justice in the country and to make the concept of justice given in preamble a reality. The approach of judiciary has been progressive in this regard and it has shown through its decisions that justice is an essential ingredient of a developed and law abiding society. In cases like Maneka Gandhi v. UOI, right of liberty the court has enforced the concept of social justice.

CONCLUSION

To conclude we would state that enforcement of justice serves as a catalyst for better political life of a nation. For better democracy we need better implementation of justice. Without presence of all forms of justice any society can't develop as a constitutional society therefore keeping it in mind framers of our constitution included this concept in the preamble as well as in part III and IV of the Indian Constitution. There is strong need for coordination among all three organs of the government to

establish a system based on justifiable approach. Ambedkar's Ideas on Social Justice A Just society is that society in which ascending sense of reverence and descending sense of contempt is dissolved into the creation of a compassionate society. Dr B.R. Ambedker Justice is a very complex concept, as it has a number of sources and dimensions. It has been examined by different people from different viewpoints within the limits of the time, place and circumstances they lived in. Social justice is one of the dimensions of the concept of justice that stands for organization of society based on the principles of equality, liberty and fraternity. Its greater emphasis is on the principle of equality, both social and economic, and fraternity with a view to create such human social conditions that ensure free and fair development of all human beings. As such, the concept of social justice sometimes require unequal or preferential treatment for certain sections of the population, which have been deprived of certain values for ages, with a view to bring them on an equal footing with other sections of the population. Ambedkar's concept of social justice stands for the liberty, equality and fraternity of all human beings. He stood for a social system that is based on right relations between man and man in all spheres of his life. As a rationalist and humanist, he did not approve of any type of hypocrisy, injustice and exploitation of man by man in the name of religion. He stood for a religion that is based on universal principles of morality and is applicable to all times, to all countries and to all races. It must be in accord with reason and must be based on the basic tenets of liberty, equality and fraternity. He considered the caste system as the greatest evil of Hindu religion. The Varna system according to him is the root cause of all inequality and is also the parent of the caste system and un-touchability. Ambedkar stood for a social system in which man's status is based on his merit and achievements and where no one is noble or untouchable because of his/her birth. He advocated the policy of preferential treatment for the socially oppressed and economically exploited people of the country. The Constitution of India, which was drafted under his chairmanship, contains a number of provisions that enjoins the state to secure to all its citizens, justice, social, economic and political, along with liberty, equality and fraternity. It also contains a number of provisions that guarantee a preferential treatment to the downtrodden people in various sectors. Article 17 of the Indian Constitution declares un-touchability act as abolished. Ambedkar, in his speech before the Constituent Assembly for the passage of the Constitution, said 'I have completed my work; I wish there should be a sunrise even tomorrow. The new Bharat has got political freedom, but it is yet to raise the sun of social and economic liberty.'

In 1912, Jawaharlal Nehru finished reading law in England and returned to practice at the Allahabad High Court. He joined the chambers of his father Motilal Nehru, then the doyen of the Allahabad Bar. But Nehru found litigation limited, dull and not intellectually stimulating. He would soon turn to politics.

Years later, as prime minister, Nehru's vision of social justice and the constitutional role of courts in helping achieve it shaped public law discourse in Independent India. For Nehru, the Constitution was foremost a roadmap for creating a socialist democratic society. But in the early years after Independence, the judiciary's views on social justice issues such as land acquisition and compensation clashed with his. A little over a decade after Nehru's death, however, the Supreme Court adopted his vision of social justice through the jurisprudence of Justices PN Bhagwati and Krishna Iyer

COOPERATIVE RIGHTS

The Supreme Court's interpretation of the judiciary's constitutional role as an active participant in democratic social change started in 1975 when Iyer and Bhagwati introduced an expansive interpretation of *locus standi* that changed forever the courts' approach to social-economic justice.

Bhagwati's judgements in Fertilizer Corporation Kamgar Union, SP Gupta v President of India and People's Union for Democratic Rights cases in the early 80s evolved the courts' approach from going by the traditional individualism of locus standi to recognising collective rights through public interest litigation, or PIL. Such an interpretation felled many cumbersome statutory processes, making it easier for socio-economically weaker citizens to access justice. In his Hussainara Khatoon judgment of 1979, Bhagwati addressed the plight of the poor caught in the criminal justice system, the dismal condition of jails, and the fact that under trials languished behind bars because they could not afford bail. He reasoned that protection of human rights and dignity, as part of the right to life, was paramount. So, the court must take cognizance of such abuses without being impeded by technical procedures.

In public interest On September 18, 1982, Bhagwati decided the People's Union of Democratic Rights case. It was brought through a writ petition arguing that the contractors building Asian Games projects were suppressing the rights of workmen. In his judgment, Bhagwati rebuked early critics of the PIL. There is a misapprehension in the minds of some lawyers, journalists and men in public life that public interest litigation is unnecessarily cluttering up files of the court. This is, to our mind, a totally perverse view smacking of elitist and status quoist approach. Millions of persons belonging to the deprived and vulnerable sections of humanity are looking to the courts for improving their life conditions and making basic human rights meaningful for them. If the sugar barons and the alcohol kings have the fundamental right to carry on their business and to fatten their purses by exploiting the consuming public, have the Chamars belonging to the lowest strata of society no fundamental right to earn an honest living through their sweat and hustle.

The Constitution-makers have given us one of the most remarkable documents in history for ushering in a new socio-economic order and the Constitution which they have forged for us has a social purpose and an economic mission and therefore every word or phrase in the Constitution must be interpreted in a manner which would advance the socio-economic objective of the Constitution. Bhagwati imagined judges developing law that would promote the socialist democratic project of securing justice. It was not enough to curtail excessive state power through judicial review, the courts had the duty to actively help achieve socio-economic goals as prescribed in the Directive Principles of State Policy. That the courts readily accepted challenges to acquisition of land from zamindars disturbed Nehru as it hindered radical land reform. In 1951, he moved the First Constitutional Amendment and added Articles 31A and 31B to the Ninth Schedule to protect laws acquiring zamindar land from judicial challenge. Justifying the legislation, the prime minister said: The High Court brings in Article 14, of all articles; to apply it to a question of land reforms... Here I am reminded that one has to respect the majesty of the law. The majesty of the law is such that it looks with an even eye on the millionaire and the beggar. But the millionaire has not much incentive to steal a loaf of bread, while the starving beggar has. This business of the equality may very well, mean, as it has come to mean often enough, the making of existing inequalities rigid by law. This is a dangerous thing and it is still more dangerous in a changing society. It is completely opposed to the whole structure and method of this Constitution and what is laid down in the Directive Principles.

Bhagwati invoked this Nehruvian idea of equality and justice in his dissenting opinion in the Minerva Mills case of 1980. The case related to a challenge to the 42nd Constitutional Amendment of 1976, which made two key changes to the Constitution. One, that no constitutional amendment made by Parliament could be tested through judicial review. Two, legislation securing the Directive Principle of preventing, for common good, the concentration of wealth could not be voided on the grounds of

violating the right to equality and the right to freedom of speech and expression. Crusaded against Hindu customs such as sati, polygamy, child marriage and the caste system. In 1828, he set up the BrahmoSabha, a movement of reformist Bengali Brahmins to fight against social evils.

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THE ROLE OF JUDICIARY IN PROTECTING DEMOCRACY IN INDIA**Dr. Radhakrishna**

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Abstract

The judiciary in India plays an essential role in safeguarding the democratic framework established by the Constitution. As the guardian of the Constitution, the Indian judiciary ensures that the fundamental rights of citizens are protected and that the law is applied impartially, without interference from the executive or legislature. Through its power of judicial review, the judiciary can challenge unconstitutional laws or government actions, ensuring that no entity holds unchecked power. Landmark cases such as Kesavananda Bharati and Maneka Gandhi have reinforced the judiciary's role in upholding the basic structure of the Constitution and protecting civil liberties, ensuring that democratic principles are preserved. Furthermore, the judiciary has been instrumental in addressing social justice issues, using mechanisms like public interest litigation (PIL) to address matters that may not have been adequately addressed by the legislative or executive branches. This has expanded the access to justice for marginalized groups and reinforced the democratic ideal of equality. The judiciary's role extends beyond mere adjudication; it also influences electoral reforms and governance issues, like ensuring transparency and holding political leaders accountable for corruption. However, challenges such as case backlogs and pressures on judicial independence continue to affect its efficiency. Despite these challenges, the Indian judiciary remains a cornerstone of democracy, as it ensures that the rights of individuals are protected, and the separation of powers is maintained. Thus, the judiciary's ability to provide impartial justice and review legislative and executive actions strengthens the democratic ethos of India. Through its independent functioning, the judiciary ensures that democracy is not just a theoretical concept but a practical reality for Indian citizens.

Keywords: Role, Judiciary, Protect, Democracy, India.

INTRODUCTION:

Democracy in India is founded on the principles of representation, equality, and liberty. As the world's largest democracy, India's political system is based on the values enshrined in its Constitution, which ensures that sovereignty resides with the people. The government is elected by the people through universal suffrage, where every adult citizen has the right to vote, and the elected representatives are accountable to the public. The system is designed to reflect the diversity of the country, incorporating multiple parties, languages, religions, and cultures. India's democracy is built on periodic elections, fundamental rights, and the rule of law. It also involves a system of checks and balances, with distinct branches of government—the executive, legislature, and judiciary—ensuring that power is not concentrated in a single entity, and that democratic freedoms are preserved for all citizens India.

The judiciary in India plays a crucial role in maintaining the rule of law and protecting the rights of citizens. It is an independent body, separate from the executive and legislative branches, which ensures checks and balances within the political system. The judicial structure includes the Supreme Court, High Courts, and subordinate courts. The Supreme Court is the highest authority, with the power to interpret the Constitution, settle disputes between states or between the state and central government, and safeguard fundamental rights. The judiciary's primary function is judicial review, which allows it to declare laws or executive actions unconstitutional if they violate the Constitution. In addition, through public interest litigation, it has become a tool for addressing social justice issues and holding the government accountable. The independence of the judiciary is essential for the preservation of democracy, as it ensures the protection of individual rights and maintains the balance of power

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

This study explores the Role of Judiciary in Protecting Democracy in India.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This study is based on secondary sources of data such as articles, books, journals, research papers, websites and other sources.

THE ROLE OF JUDICIARY IN PROTECTING DEMOCRACY IN INDIA

In the Indian democratic system, the judiciary plays a pivotal role in preserving the constitutional framework and ensuring the protection of democratic values. The Constitution of India, adopted in 1950, lays the foundation for the political and legal structure of the country. The judiciary, one of the three branches of government, has a unique and powerful role in maintaining the checks and balances required for the smooth functioning of democracy. This role is vital in safeguarding the rights and freedoms of citizens, maintaining the rule of law, and ensuring that the other branches of government—executive and legislature—do not overstep their constitutional boundaries. The Indian judiciary has evolved over time into an institution that not only interprets laws but also shapes them. Its role in the protection of democracy extends beyond the realm of legal rulings; it includes protecting the fundamental rights of citizens, maintaining accountability of public officials, safeguarding the separation of powers, and ensuring that democratic processes are not undermined. Given the complexities of Indian society, with its diversity of religions, cultures, and languages, the judiciary's function in upholding democracy becomes even more crucial.

The importance of the judiciary in India's democracy is enshrined in its constitutional framework. The Constitution of India provides for an independent judiciary, which is crucial for preventing any potential misuse of power. The framers of the Constitution recognized that a strong, impartial judiciary would be essential to prevent authoritarianism, safeguard the fundamental rights of citizens, and preserve democratic institutions. The judiciary's independence ensures that the government, whether at the state or central level, remains within the bounds of the law, and that no branch of government is allowed to function arbitrarily. One of the most significant ways the judiciary protects democracy is by upholding the fundamental rights guaranteed by the Constitution. The Indian Constitution guarantees a set of rights under Part III, including the right to equality, the right to freedom of speech and expression, the right to life and personal liberty, and the right to freedom of religion, among others. These rights are essential to the functioning of a democracy, as they provide citizens with the tools to challenge government actions and express their views without fear of retribution. The judiciary has the responsibility of ensuring that these rights are not violated, even when there are pressures from the executive or the legislature. Over the years, the judiciary has often intervened to protect individual rights from arbitrary actions of the state, thus reinforcing the democratic principles enshrined in the Constitution.

A landmark case that highlights the judiciary's role in protecting fundamental rights is the *Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala* case (1973), in which the Supreme Court ruled that the basic structure of the Constitution could not be altered by amendments. The case affirmed that while the legislature has the power to amend the Constitution, it cannot alter its fundamental framework. This judgment reinforced the importance of the judiciary in protecting the Constitution and ensuring that no party or government could undermine the democratic structure. It also emphasized that the judiciary is the guardian of the Constitution, and that it would play an active role in safeguarding democracy. The judiciary also plays an essential role in ensuring accountability and transparency in governance. In a democracy, the rule of law is paramount, and public officials, regardless of their position, must be held accountable for their actions. The judiciary has the authority to scrutinize the actions of the executive and legislature, and it

can strike down laws or government actions that violate the Constitution. Through judicial review, the judiciary acts as a safeguard against arbitrary or unconstitutional actions by the government. For example, the judiciary has the power to intervene when the executive oversteps its bounds, such as in cases of executive orders or actions that violate citizens' rights.

The role of the judiciary in protecting democracy is also reflected in its involvement in electoral matters. The judiciary often intervenes in cases related to electoral malpractices, corruption, and violations of electoral laws. In a democracy, free and fair elections are the cornerstone of representative government. The judiciary has been instrumental in addressing issues related to the electoral process, such as voter suppression, campaign finance, and the role of political parties. It ensures that the election process remains fair and transparent, which is crucial for maintaining the legitimacy of the democratic system. Judicial intervention in electoral disputes, as seen in cases related to the validity of elections, helps maintain the integrity of the democratic process. Moreover, the judiciary has a critical role in preserving the separation of powers, which is essential for any democracy. The Constitution of India divides the functions of government into three distinct branches: the executive, the legislature, and the judiciary. Each of these branches is meant to function independently, and the judiciary is tasked with ensuring that the other branches do not encroach upon each other's domain. For instance, the judiciary can strike down laws passed by the legislature if they are deemed unconstitutional, and it can ensure that the executive does not exercise powers beyond its constitutional mandate. This system of checks and balances is fundamental to the protection of democracy, as it prevents any single branch of government from becoming too powerful.

The role of the judiciary in protecting democracy is not limited to the protection of individual rights or the maintenance of the rule of law; it also extends to social justice. The judiciary has increasingly become a forum for addressing issues of social inequality and discrimination. Through public interest litigation (PIL), individuals and organizations can approach the courts to seek redress for issues related to human rights, environmental protection, and social justice. This has allowed the judiciary to play an active role in advocating for marginalized communities and ensuring that the government fulfills its constitutional obligations towards the welfare of all citizens. The judiciary has been instrumental in advancing social justice by providing remedies for those who have been deprived of their rights, whether they are from disadvantaged castes, minorities, or other marginalized groups. An example of the judiciary's role in promoting social justice is the *Vishaka v. State of Rajasthan* case (1997), in which the Supreme Court issued guidelines for the protection of women from sexual harassment in the workplace. This case highlighted the judiciary's capacity to address evolving societal issues and ensure that laws and policies reflect the values of equality and justice. The judiciary's role in expanding the scope of fundamental rights to cover contemporary concerns is a reflection of its broader responsibility to protect democracy and ensure that the law adapts to changing societal needs.

In addition to these aspects, the judiciary in India plays a key role in preserving the democratic spirit of the Constitution through its interpretation of its provisions. The Indian judiciary, especially the Supreme Court, has a history of progressive judicial activism, where it has taken proactive measures to interpret the Constitution in ways that safeguard the principles of democracy. The role of the judiciary is not confined to the mechanical interpretation of laws; it also involves a broader responsibility of interpreting the Constitution in a manner that aligns with its democratic values. For example, the judiciary has played a critical role in expanding the scope of the right to life and personal liberty under Article 21 of the Constitution, interpreting it to include a wide range of rights such as the right to privacy, the right to a clean environment, and the right to live with dignity.

The judiciary's independence, however, is not without challenges. In recent years, there have been concerns regarding the increasing politicization of the judiciary, which could undermine its ability to function as an independent institution. There have been instances where the executive and legislature have sought to influence judicial appointments or challenged the decisions of the judiciary, particularly in cases related to political power. The judiciary's role in protecting democracy is thus contingent upon its ability to maintain its independence and resist external pressures. The collegium system, which is currently in place for judicial appointments, is one mechanism designed to preserve the independence of the judiciary, although it has been the subject of debate and criticism.

In recent years, the judiciary in India has played a crucial role in upholding democracy by ensuring justice and checking the power of the executive and legislature. Statistically, the role of the judiciary in protecting democracy can be seen through various avenues, including its decisions on matters of human rights, corruption, and government overreach. India's judicial system is pivotal in maintaining constitutional values. The Supreme Court, as the guardian of the Constitution, has delivered several landmark rulings, often countering executive or legislative actions that could undermine democratic principles. For example, the judiciary's intervention in cases related to electoral reforms, the right to privacy, and freedom of speech has been instrumental in safeguarding civil liberties. As of 2023, the Supreme Court has been actively involved in ensuring accountability in governance, often holding political figures accountable for corruption, and supporting transparency in public administration. One key aspect of judicial involvement is judicial accountability, which ensures that judges make decisions without fear or favor, thus upholding public trust. Reports indicate that in India, efforts have been made to improve judicial transparency and accountability, including the establishment of online platforms for accessing court decisions. These steps are essential for reinforcing democratic values by making the judicial system more accessible to the public.

However, challenges remain. There is a noted concern about the delay in justice due to a heavy backlog of cases in Indian courts. This not only affects the speed of legal remedies but also the overall perception of judicial efficiency in protecting democracy. In 2023, the backlog of cases in Indian courts stood at over 4.5 crore cases, highlighting the urgent need for judicial reforms. Furthermore, the judiciary's independence has been a subject of ongoing discussion. The rising pressures from political entities and attempts to undermine judicial independence pose risks to democratic integrity. Despite these challenges, India's judiciary continues to play a pivotal role in protecting the rule of law by checking government excesses and ensuring the protection of fundamental rights.

1. Case on Electoral Freebies:

One of the most significant recent cases is the one concerning the legality of pre-election promises made by political parties, often termed as "electoral freebies." In 2022, Advocate Ashwini Kumar Upadhyay petitioned the Supreme Court to address the practice of political parties making promises of freebies to voters without any financial assessments. The petition argued that such promises distort fair elections and could be classified as corrupt practices under the Representation of the People Act, 1951, and even as bribery under the Indian Penal Code. The issue at hand was whether the practice of promising such freebies could be seen as an unfair electoral tactic that undermines the integrity of the election process. While the Court acknowledged the negative consequences of such practices on the electoral system, it also recognized the need to balance welfare schemes with public good. In August 2022, the matter was referred to a larger bench of three judges for further deliberation. On November 23, 2023, the Court revisited the case, where it reviewed the petitions, showing a clear commitment to ensuring that electoral promises do not violate the principles of fairness and democracy. This case is significant because it

addresses the intersection of electoral integrity, financial accountability, and democratic fairness, demonstrating the judiciary's critical role in enforcing transparency in the electoral process. It also underscores the importance of the judiciary in safeguarding electoral democracy by ensuring that parties are held accountable for promises made to the electorate and that such promises do not lead to undue influence over voters through unmanageable state expenditures.

2. Federalism and Delhi's Governance:

Another case that showcases the judiciary's role in preserving democratic values is the Supreme Court's ruling on the governance structure of Delhi, in particular, the National Capital Territory (NCT) of Delhi. The case revolves around the interpretation of Article 239AA of the Indian Constitution, which outlines the relationship between the central government and the Delhi government. The issue was whether the Delhi government had full legislative powers over services within the state, or if the Union had overriding control, particularly over the appointment and transfer of civil servants. In its ruling in 2023, a Constitution Bench of the Supreme Court emphatically upheld that the Delhi Legislative Assembly indeed had legislative powers, but with certain limitations. The ruling reinforced the concept of asymmetric federalism, which recognizes that Delhi's unique status requires a balance between autonomy for the Delhi government and the overarching authority of the Union government. The Court emphasized that an accountable government must have control over civil servants to ensure effective governance and democratic accountability to the people of Delhi. This case is critical because it reaffirms the importance of federalism in India's governance model and protects the democratic right of residents of Delhi to have their elected representatives hold authority over governance within the state. The judgment ensures that the Delhi government remains accountable to its electorate, reinforcing democratic principles by making sure that there is no undue interference from the central government in local affairs, particularly in administrative decisions

Case Study 3: Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala (1973)

The *Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala* case (1973) is one of the most pivotal rulings in the history of the Indian judiciary, and it remains a cornerstone in understanding the judiciary's role in protecting democracy in India. This case dealt with the power of the Indian Parliament to amend the Constitution and the scope of judicial review. In this case, the Supreme Court of India was tasked with determining whether Parliament had the power to amend any part of the Constitution, including the fundamental rights section. The petitioner, Kesavananda Bharati, a religious leader from Kerala, challenged the validity of the Kerala Land Reforms Act that sought to limit the amount of land that could be owned by an individual, claiming that it violated his fundamental rights. In the course of the case, the Court expanded the scope of judicial review, which eventually led to the landmark declaration that Parliament could not alter the "basic structure" of the Constitution.

The ruling, delivered by a 13-judge bench, asserted that while Parliament had the power to amend the Constitution under Article 368, such amendments were subject to the limitation that they could not disturb the Constitution's basic structure. This decision protected the core principles of the Constitution, such as the rule of law, democracy, secularism, and judicial review, from potential erosion through political maneuvering.

This judgment had profound implications for India's democracy. By asserting the judiciary's authority to review and strike down amendments that violated the basic structure, the Court ensured that fundamental democratic principles would remain intact even if the legislature, influenced by political forces, sought to change them. It solidified the judiciary's role as a protector of the Constitution,

ensuring that the separation of powers and the checks and balances integral to a functioning democracy would not be easily undermined by any government in power.

The *Kesavananda Bharati* case stands as a beacon of judicial activism in India. It was a direct assertion of the judiciary's independence, reinforcing its role as a counterbalance to the other branches of government. It ensured that any attempt to alter the democratic framework of the country would be scrutinized by the judiciary, thus protecting the principles of democracy and rule of law.

Case Study 4: Right to Privacy Judgment - K.S. Puttaswamy v. Union of India (2017)

In another landmark case, the Supreme Court of India, in 2017, recognized the right to privacy as a fundamental right under the Constitution in the case *K.S. Puttaswamy v. Union of India*. This judgment was significant not only for its immediate implications on privacy but also for its wider impact on the protection of individual freedoms in India, thus reinforcing the role of the judiciary in safeguarding democracy. The case was triggered by concerns regarding the government's Aadhaar scheme, which involved the collection of biometric data from citizens for the purpose of providing them with welfare services. Petitioners, led by retired judge K.S. Puttaswamy, argued that the Aadhaar system violated citizens' right to privacy, which they argued was an essential part of the right to life and personal liberty under Article 21 of the Constitution. In a unanimous verdict, the nine-judge bench of the Supreme Court held that the right to privacy is a fundamental right, implicitly guaranteed by the Constitution, particularly under Articles 14 (right to equality), 19 (freedom of speech), and 21 (right to life and liberty). This judgment was a reaffirmation of the judiciary's role in protecting the basic freedoms of citizens against potential encroachments by the state.

The *Puttaswamy* case had wide-ranging implications for India's democracy. The judgment redefined the scope of privacy rights, considering the increasing digitalization and surveillance capabilities of the state and private entities. It put the judiciary at the forefront of protecting citizens' autonomy and personal freedoms, ensuring that individual rights would not be sacrificed in the name of state policies or national security. The judgment also addressed the tension between state interests (such as security and welfare) and individual rights, emphasizing that any state action that impinges on privacy must meet a strict test of necessity, proportionality, and legality. Furthermore, this case emphasized the judiciary's role in interpreting the Constitution in light of contemporary issues. In the face of growing state surveillance and digital data collection, the Supreme Court balanced the need for technological and administrative efficiency with the protection of personal liberty, ensuring that democracy in India would remain vibrant and free from excessive state control.

The *Puttaswamy* case also had significant political implications. It curtailed the state's ability to compel citizens to provide biometric data without their informed consent. The judgment not only checked the overreach of the executive but also acted as a safeguard for democratic values, ensuring that citizens retained control over their personal information in a digital age. Both the *Kesavananda Bharati* and *Puttaswamy* cases underscore the judiciary's indispensable role in protecting democracy. They highlight how the Indian judiciary has taken an active role in ensuring that the core principles of democracy—such as rule of law, individual freedoms, and judicial review—are upheld. These cases also illustrate how the judiciary has, at critical junctures, intervened to prevent the erosion of democratic institutions and safeguard the constitutional rights of citizens. Through these decisions, the judiciary has reinforced its role as the ultimate protector of democracy in India.

CONCLUSION:

The judiciary plays a pivotal role in preserving the democratic fabric of India by ensuring justice, upholding the Constitution, and acting as a check on both the executive and legislative branches.

Through its power of judicial review, it can invalidate laws or actions that violate the Constitution, thus protecting fundamental rights and maintaining the balance of power. Landmark rulings have reinforced the protection of civil liberties, ensuring that the democratic ideals of equality, freedom, and justice are upheld for all citizens. Moreover, the judiciary's involvement in social justice issues through mechanisms like Public Interest Litigation (PIL) has expanded access to justice, particularly for marginalized communities. Despite facing challenges such as a backlog of cases and pressures on its independence, the judiciary remains a key player in shaping India's democracy. Its commitment to the rule of law and its ability to address both legal and socio-political issues ensure that democracy remains robust and resilient. The role of the judiciary in India is crucial for the survival and flourishing of democracy. By providing checks on the other branches of government and safeguarding individual rights, it ensures that the values of democracy are not only preserved but also protected from any attempts to undermine them.

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YOUTH POLITICAL PARTICIPATION IN INDIA AS CONSTITUTIONAL RIGHTS**Dr. Shivaiah M**

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Abstract

"Democracy' and 'free and fair election' are inseparable twins. There is almost an in severable umbilical cord joining them. The little man's ballot and not the bullet of those who want to capture power is the heartbeat of democracy. Path of the little man to the polling booth should be free and unhindered, and his freedom to elect a candidate of his choice is the foundation of a free and fair election. - Justice, Arijit Pasayat, Supreme Court of India.

Webster's dictionary defines 'election' as "the act or process of choosing a person for an office, position or membership by voting".

According to Black's law dictionary 'election' means choice of persons to fill public office means the expression by, vote of he will of the people or of a numerous body of electors.

Meaning "rule by the people," democracy is a system of government that not only allows but requires the participation of the people in the political process to function properly. U.S.

President ABRAHAM LINCKEN-in his famed 1863 Addressing at Gettysburg may have best defined democracy as a "Government of the people, by the people, for the people.

Semantically, the term democracy comes from the Greek words for "people" dēmos and "rule" karatos. However, achieving and preserving a government by the people—a "popular" government—is far more complicated than the concept's semantic simplicity might imply. In creating the legal framework under which the democracy will function, typically a constitution, several crucial political and practical questions must be answered.

Is "rule by the people" even appropriate for the given state Do the inherent freedoms of a democracy justify dealing with its complex bureaucracy and electoral processes, or would the Streamlined predictability of a monarchy, for example, is preferable.

Assuming a preference for democracy, which residents of the country, state, or town should enjoy the political status of full citizenship? Simply stated, who are the "people" in the "government by the people" equation? In the Indians, for example, the constitutionally established doctrine of birthright citizenship provides that any person born on India. Indian soil automatically becomes a Indian citizen. Other democracies are more restrictive in bestowing full citizenship.

MEANING OF DEMOCRACY:

- **Rtd. Political Science Professor H.V.Venugopal** : People participation in the government activities like selection of the leaders, frame of the policies and enjoying with the rights and duties.
- **Famous slogan American President Abraham Lincoln**: From the people, for the people and by the people it's called Democracy.
- **According to Dr.B.R Ambedkar** : My ideal would e a society based on Liberty, Equality and fraternity, which is only another name for democracy. Democracy is not merely a form of Government.
- **Mahatma Gandhiji** : In the democracy which envisaged a democracy established by non-violence, there will be equal freedom for all.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- Encourage to the Political Parties

- Supporting to youth mind
- Improvement of New administration skills
- Create in to The New Political Leaders
- Share with new political Knowledge
- Sharpness of legislative- Executive and Judiciary
- Encouraging to Liberty, Equality and Fraternity among the people
- Selection of the good Governance and Leaders

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

- Young Voters very interestingly participation in voting system
- Someone's youths are cannot interested in politics
- So many young people's contested in elections
- Some Rural Area voters can't voting
- System of election can't satisfied
- Election system is not a Democracy

61st Amendment Act of India 1988

Which people within the democracy should be empowered to participate in it, assuming that only adults are age 18 years and above 61st Amendment of Constitution of India

- ❖ Article 326 of the Constitution of India deals with elections to the Houses and to the State Legislative Assemblies on the basis of universal adult suffrage.
- ❖ The article before being amended by the 61st Amendment stated that any citizen of India who is 21 years or above, and who is not disqualified on any other grounds such as non-residence, crime, corrupt or illegal practices or unsoundness of mind, is eligible to vote at an election.
- ❖ The proposal to reduce the voting age to 18 years was brought about to increase the participation of the youth in the electoral process of the country.
- ❖ Today, in India about 52 lakh voters are 18 years of age and they do play a decisive role in the outcome of the elections happening in India.
- ❖ In 2011, there was a talk of reducing the age further to 16 years but nothing has come of it so far.
- ❖ The Constitution (Sixty-first Amendment) Act, 1988 was introduced in the Lok Sabha on 13th December 1988 by the then Water Resources Minister B. Shankaranand.
- ❖ It was debated and passed by the lower house on 15th The Rajya Sabha passed the bill on 20th December. As per law, more than half the state legislatures had to ratify the bill and this was duly obtained. Only five states, Jammu & Kashmir, Punjab, Nagaland, Tamil Nadu and Tripura did not ratify.
- ❖ The bill received the presidential assent on 28th March 1989 when the then President of India assented it.
- ❖ Thus, the act came into force on 28th March 1989 and from that day onwards, any citizen who is otherwise qualified could participate in the democratic processes in India from the age of 18 years.

DEMOCRACY IS THE BEST FORM OF GOVERNMENT

Allowed to fully participate in the political process, should all adults be included For example, women in the India's were not allowed to vote in national elections. A democracy that excludes too many of the governed from taking part in what is supposed to be their government runs the risk of becoming an aristocracy government by a small, privileged ruling class or an oligarchy government by an elite,

typically wealthy, few. If, as one of the foundational principles of democracy holds, the majority rules, what will a “proper” majority be? A majority of all citizens or a majority of citizens who vote only? When issues, as they inevitably will, divide the people, should the wishes of the majority always prevail, or should, as in the case of the American Civil Rights Movement, minorities be empowered to overcome majority rule? Most importantly, what legal or legislative mechanisms should be created to prevent the democracy from becoming a victim of what one of America’s Founding Fathers, James Madison, questioned “the tyranny of the majority. Finally, how likely is it that a majority of the people will continue to believe that democracy is the best form of government for them. For a democracy to survive it must retain the substantial support of both the people and the leaders they choose. History has shown that democracy is a particularly delicate institution. In fact, of the 120 new democracies that have emerged around the world since 1960, nearly half have resulted in failed states or have been replaced by other, typically more authoritarian forms of government. It is therefore essential that democracies be designed to respond quickly and appropriately to the internal and external factors that will inevitably threaten them.

IMPACT OF FIRST-TIME VOTERS

The youth voting for the first time have shown prominent interest in politics and believe that without their involvement in voting, they do not have a say in the governance of the country and cannot be held accountable. Balaji 19 years old, from Tumkur was thrilled to vote for the first time. “The thrill to be able to vote for the first time and have a say on the governance of the country was quite amazing, but it didn’t last long; it was a short process,” she recounted. Balaji chose a candidate aligned with her ideals but wished for more options closer to her ideology. “I do wish that there were more options, someone who was closer to my ideology,” she said. Aarushi hopes the elected government will prioritize public welfare over personal gain.

NEWLY YOUTH PARTICIPATION IN ELECTION

The Election Commission of India (ECI) reported that only 40 per cent of eligible 18-19-year-olds have registered to vote in the 2024 elections nationwide. There are 18.5 million voters aged 18-19 who will be casting their ballots for the first time. A lot of the people were not able to receive their voter ID cards in time to cast their votes.

In Dakshin Kolkata, under Phase 6 of the ongoing elections, Ronit Ghosh, aged 20, awaits a deep sense of empowerment. “I feel like I have taken a stand and followed through with my right to choose my candidate in the Indian Legislature,” he stated. Many of his friends faced challenges voting for geographical and logistical reasons, but Ronit was fortunate that his voting date coincided with his summer vacation. “For me, I was lucky my election dates were after the start of my summer vacation, so it was not much of an issue for me,” he explained. Ronit believes in the importance of voting as a civic duty. “We should exercise our rights given to us, not just for us – but for every single citizen of the country,” he concluded.

CIVIC DUTY AND RESPONSIBILITY

These first-time voters, despite facing various challenges, are united by their commitment to making informed and independent choices. They embody a generation that understands the power of their vote and the importance of participating in the democratic process. As they cast their ballots, they do so with hopes for a better, more accountable government that will show the country towards a brighter future.

WHAT IS THE IMPORTANT YOUTH PARTICIPATION IN INDIAN ELECTION

Man is an emotional animal. And humans are also social animals. Because many aspects of human life are related to the society. Every aspect of a human being is involved in political activities. We call these

activities related to humans “politics” in one language. Politics is like a game. In which many teams and many players are present in each team, but only one wins. Similarly many political parties contest elections and the winning party is the ruling party. The political system of India works under the Constitution. Some politicians and government employees have spoiled the image of the country’s politics and the condition of the country. Greed, corruption, poverty, illiteracy have tainted Indian politics. Due to which the image of the leaders or the image of the administration towards the public is being tarnished. It can remove the nation or society from problems like unemployment, corruption and poverty, if seen; politics has also been the father of these big problems. Any area cannot be reviewed from one point of view, Mahatma Gandhi had said that if you want to change your society, you want to make sacrifices for it, and then youth should come into politics. It is very important for good and honest people to enter politics for the development of the country, and apart from a strong one-sided government, a strong opposition also makes the governments committed to serve the interests of the society. Politics is considered to be the game of clever people, who try to exploit their own temptations in the name of the interest of the nation and the state.

WHAT INTENSITY ARE THE ELECTIONS DETAINED

In the political world of India, the political party won after the election is called a process of gaining power from the ruling party. This political election process ranges from village, district, tehsil, to the election of the country and we all know that all elections are controlled and supervised by the Election Commission. The formation of a successful government is possible here only through the process of Indian politics and elections. The government is helpful in the development work of the country and the progress of the nation. The first general election in India was held in 1951 after independence from the British. The Indian National Congress won India’s first election after independence.

PARLIAMENTARY SYSTEM OF GOVERNMENT

Indian politics works within a parliamentary and constitutional framework, with the head of government, the President and the Prime Minister representing the country. India is a parliamentary federal democratic republic country. The polity of India works under a diarchy, with one acting as the central government and the other as the state government.

In a democratic country like our India, the parliamentary form reflects the functioning of the government. And the Prime Minister of the country is considered as the government. Although the head of the country is the President, but the entire command is in the hands of the Prime Minister. You must know that the President is the supreme citizen of the country.

YOUTH’S INTERVENTION IN POLITICS IS NECESSARY

In our country of India, people are completely free to choose the representative of their choice through general elections. Every person of the country who has completed 18 years of age has the right to exercise his vote freely or to choose his representative as per his wish. After every five years, there is a general election of the country, in which you can choose your representative freely.

Today every citizen of India understands his good and bad very well. The youth will have to widen the scope of their thinking beyond communalism and politics. The youth will have to proceed very carefully in this matter. And don’t get swayed by any such emotion and take a decision after thinking.

There are other things like unemployment, different issues of the country and things like bribery to get place in government jobs are also the reasons to keep the youth away from the country. That is why we have to guide our youth from time to time. So that they can identify right and wrong and help in taking their country forward and on the path of progress.

- There are at least 1.82 crore first-time voters in the electoral rolls.

- There are 97.8 crore eligible voters of which 49.72 crore are male voters and 47.1 crore are female voters.
- More than 2 lakh registered voters were over 100 years of age.
- There are 19.74 crore young voters in the 20 to 29 age group.
- The poll body said in the 2022-23 election cycle, cash seizure surged over 800% to Rs 3,400 crore in 11 states compared to five years ago. "Enforcement agencies are directed to crack down on illicit money, liquor, drugs, and freebies, staying vigilant against disruptive methods," the poll body said.
- Out of the total 543 seats, 412 are for general candidates, 84 are reserved for Scheduled Caste (SC) representatives and 47 for Scheduled Tribe (ST) representatives.
- Over 2,100 general, police, and expenditure observers are being deployed for elections.
- Over 1.5 crore polling officials have been deployed and 10.5 lakh polling stations have been set up.
- Over 55 lakh EVMs will be deployed.
- Over 4 lakh vehicles will be used.
- The poll body has conducted 17 general elections, over 400 assembly polls, 16 presidential polls, and 16 vice-presidential polls.
- Over 48,000 transgenders are eligible to vote in the upcoming Lok Sabha elections.
- The number of transgender voters in the 2019 Lok Sabha polls was 39,075 with the maximum number of them from Uttar Pradesh (7,797) followed by Tamil Nadu (5,793) and Karnataka (4,826).
- A total of 88.4 lakh people with disabilities have been registered in the electoral roll.

Here are some good reasons why the Young should vote and be proud participants in the democratic process.

SINGLE VOTE ALSO HIGHLY VALUABLE

- A lot of young voters aren't sure if their single vote would make any difference. However, each and every vote is decisive and has the power to impact the end result. Every vote cast makes a difference and every voter who marks his ballot plays a part in sustaining and bolstering democracy. There have been several instances in the electoral history of India where one vote was enough to turn the tables. In 1999, the 13-month-old government led by the then prime minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee fell after it lost the motion of confidence in the lower house of the parliament by just one vote. A more recent example where a single vote made all the difference was during the 2008 assembly elections in Rajasthan when senior Congress leader CP Joshi lost to Kalyan Singh Chauhan of BJP by a count of 62,216 to 62,215 votes.

ONE MUST VOTE TO SHEPHERD IN POSITIVE CHANGE

- A well-considered vote acts as an agent of change in a society plagued by a plethora of challenges. It is the duty of every citizen that he educates himself and others about the contemporary issues and also analyses what each candidate has to offer. The votes we cast go a long way in designing and formulating policies on issues that affect our day-to-day lives. A non-performing government or incompetent representatives cannot be shown door if voters shirk their responsibility.

LOSE THE MORAL RIGHT TO CRITICIZE GOVERNMENT IF YOU DON'T VOTE:

- Criticizing government and its policies especially on social media is the favorite pastime of many youngsters. However, if you skip your vote, you really don't deserve the right to criticize

or praise your government. You can't have an opinion on what others chose because you didn't participate in the process of electing your representative or the government. By not exercising your right to vote, you are simply giving up the chance of having a say in the political process.

DEMOCRACY CANS UTILITY ONLY IF PEOPLE VOTE:

- Despite all its follies and limitations, democracy remains the best available and the most successful form of government in the contemporary world. In order to keep it alive and functioning, the citizens must participate in elections that form the lifeblood of any democracy. By not exercising their franchise, the citizens inadvertently play a role in jeopardising democracy.

TO REPUTATION THOSE WHO LAY THEIR LIFE FOR INDIA'S INDEPENDENCE

- India attained independence in 1947 following a tough and long drawn struggle involving the sacrifices of our gallant freedom fighters. Those valiant men and women laid down their lives so that their future generations could live freely, without any foreign domination. The right to vote, therefore, becomes not only a responsibility towards the nation, but also a means to honour our past struggles. Remember, voting is a right denied to many across the globe.

CONCLUSION

In every democracy, election takes place regularly. In the globe, there are more than 100 nations where elections occur to select member of the People. The system by which citizens at regular intervals may select their representatives and switch them when they want is termed as election. Elections are a standardized process by which citizens cast votes and elect members to different government positions. Elections are the foundations. Elections are the foundation of a democracy, wherein the adult population of a nation elects the peoples representative. Commonly we are observed young voters and Represents unsatisfied in the Indian Election systems, also fake voting, selling the votes to the party and rich represents. India is world's largest democracy owing to the sheer size of its electorate. In the last general elections held in 2014, over 81 crore people were expected to cast ballots and at least 20 per cent of them were eligible to vote for the first time. Sadly, only half of these youth voters exercised their franchise. Free and fair elections are the backbone of any democracy, and therefore, it is important that everyone who's eligible marks their ballot. Voting is a right, a responsibility, and a privilege.

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GROWTH AND EVOLUTION OF DEMOCRACY AND ADMINISTRATION IN INDIA**Muniswamy Gowda M**

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Abstract

Democracy is the greatest government system in the world. Among the world 195 of Countries 93% of the Nations adopted and follow direct or indirect system of the Democracy. India is one of the largest and highest populations (nearly 147 cr. People) and constitutional parliamentary system of the government.

THE MAHAJANAPADAS, were a set of sixteen kingdoms that existed in ancient India. It all began when the tribes (janas) of the late Vedic period decided to form their own protective communities, which ultimately gave ascend to new and eternal areas of settlements called 'states' or 'janapadas.' In the sixth century BC, current Bihar and eastern Uttar Pradesh became centers of political activities as the region was not only productive but also closer to the iron production centers. iron production played a vital role in expanding the territorial states of the region. These expansions helped some of these janapadas turn into large states or mahajanapadas. Most of these mahajanapadas were monarchical in nature, while some of them were democratic states. Many prominent ancient Buddhist texts make frequent references to the 16 great kingdoms mahajanapadas that flourished between the sixth and the fourth centuries BC. These 16 kingdoms included kingdoms like Anga, Gandhara, Kuru, and Panchala, which are mentioned in the great Indian epic 'Mahabharata.' The concept of democracy finds its origins in Ancient Greece, specifically in Athens during the 5th century BC. The Athens model of democracy, known as **Direct Democracy**, allowed citizens to assemble and vote on laws and policies directly. However, it's essential to note that this form of democracy was limited, not including women, slaves, and non-citizens from contribution. The Athens Assembly, where citizens could tone of voice their opinions on various matters, showcased the premature principles of citizen engagement in governance.

Key Words: Direct Democracy, Citizens, Governance, Roman Republic, Administration, Mahajanapadas, Century. Bc, Communities, Mahabharatha, Vedic Culture, Vittal Role, Rome And Athens

INDIRECT DEMOCRACY (Representative democracy) :

Although Athens positions the stage, it was the Roman Republic that introduced the idea of representative democracy. Elected officials, representing the interests of the people, were entrusted with decision-making responsibilities. This system expected to address the challenges of direct democracy, allowing for more capable governance in a larger and more different society. The Roman Senate, consisting of elected representatives, exemplified the transition from straight to representative democracy, emphasizing the importance of consideration and representation.

THE MAHAJANAPADAS: were a set of sixteen kingdoms that existed in ancient India. It all began when the tribes (janas) of the late Vedic period decided to form their own protective communities, which ultimately gave ascend to new and eternal areas of settlements called 'states' or 'janapadas.' In the sixth century BC, current Bihar and eastern Uttar Pradesh became centers of political activities as the region was not only productive but also closer to the iron production centers. iron production played a vital role in expanding the territorial states of the region. These expansions helped some of these janapadas turn into large states or mahajanapadas. Most of these mahajanapadas were monarchical in nature, while some of them were democratic states. Many prominent ancient Buddhist texts make frequent references to the 16 great kingdoms mahajanapadas that flourished between the sixth and the

fourth centuries BC. These 16 kingdoms included kingdoms like Anga, Gandhara, Kuru, and Panchala, which are mentioned in the great Indian epic ‘Mahabharata.’

History of the Mahajanapadas: In order to settle down permanently, simple land-grabbing process was started by the tribes, which eventually turned into well-planned communities. These communities gave rise to states or janapadas and tribal identity became a major factor in defining the territory of a particular state. regularly, some of these states began to expand and hence came to be known as the mahajanapadas. Since expansion involved annexing of bordering states, certain mahajanapadas started victorious other janapadas in order to extend their kingdoms as per the kingdom’s opulence and wealth. Early stages of settlement of the tribes happened before the time of the Buddha. Hence, historical references of these can be found in ancient Buddhist texts. Many such texts talk about **16 great kingdoms** that flourished between the sixth and the fourth centuries BC. The period between the sixth and fourth centuries BC is considered particularly important in early Indian history as it witnessed the materialization of massive Indian cities, which were built after the fall of the Indus Valley culture. These massive Indian cities were home to the 16 great kingdoms described in the ancient texts. In the modern period the term mahajanapadas is often used to refer the 16 great kingdoms, which are mentioned below.

1. Magadha: Magadha was one of the most wealthy kingdoms of ancient India and one of the most well-known mahajanapadas. For many years, Pataliputra was the capital of Magadha. The kingdom was bounded by Ganges in the north, river Champa in the east, and river Son in the west. According to ancient texts, Brihadratha was the first known ruler of Magadha. The kingdom was also ruled by King Bimbisara, under whom Magadha flourished. Great Indian empires including the famous Maurya Dynasty originated in Magadha. Gautama Buddha exhausted much of his life in Magadha, hence the region is believed to hold great implication to Buddhists.

2. Gandhara : According to Hecataeus of Miletus, Purushapura or present-day Peshawar served as a grand Gandharic city. Other references pertaining to Gandhara have been made in ancient texts like Rigveda, Ramayana and Mahabharata. This great kingdom was served amiably by river Indus and its capital Taksashila housed the prominent center of learning, the Taksashila University. Scholars came to the university from all over the world in order to seek greater knowledge and wisdom. Though Gandhara was a huge kingdom on its own, it is often considered to be a part of an empire by modern-day scholars. Gandhara and Kamboja, which was one of the 16 mahajanapadas, were two provinces of a single domain.

3. Kamboja: The state of Kamboja is referred to as republican in more than a few ancient scripts. These scripts also state that there were two Kamboja settlements, a theory which is backed by modern-day historians. It is said that ancient Kamboja was positioned on either sides of the Hindukush mountain range. But clans of Kamboja are whispered to have crossed the mountain range to plant colonies in the southern side as well. These clans of people are connected with the Gandharas and Daradas and find mention in many Indian texts, including the edicts of Ashoka the Great.

4. Kuru: At the time of the Buddha, Kuru was ruled by Koravya, a titular chieftain. Its capital was Indraprastha present-day Delhi, which was known for people with resonance health and deep wisdom. The Kurus were related to people of other communities like the ‘Panchalas’ and the ‘Yadavas’ as they had matrimonial relations with them. Though Kuru kingdom was a well-known monarchical state in the ancient world, the 6th and 5th centuries BCE saw the formation of republican form of government in the land of Kuru. Kautilya’s ‘Arthashastra,’ which was written in Sanskrit in the 4th century BCE, also states that the Kurus followed the king consul constitution.

5. Kosala : The kingdom of Kosala was located close to the kingdom of Magadha. With Ayodhya as its capital, Kosala was hurdle by river Ganges in the south, river Gandak in the east, and the Himalaya mountains in the north. According to Vedic texts, Kosala was the biggest and most commanding kingdom ever in history. At the time of the Buddha and Mahavira, Kosala kingdom was ruled by King Prasenajit. After a sequence of tactical moves for domination by Kosala and Magadha, the kingdom of Kosala was ultimately merged with Magadha, when Kosala was being ruled by Vidudabha.

6. Malla: The Mallas of the Malla kingdom are frequently described as authoritative people who dwelled in Northern South Asia. Many Buddhist texts pass on to the kingdom as a republican dominion made up of nine territories. Like Kuru, Malla kingdom too had monarchical forms of government, but later moved towards the republican form of government. Ancient cities like Kusinara and Pava, which belonged to the Malla kingdom, are well thought-out extremely important by Jains and Buddhists. While Lord Mahavira had his last meal at Kusinara, Gauthama Buddha had his last meal at Pava. Both Kusinara and Pava are believed to have hosted Buddha for a long period of time.

7. Panchala : The Panchala kingdom was located east of the Kuru kingdom, between river Ganges and the mountain ranges of the Himalayas. Panchala was divided into two parts, namely Dakshina-Panchala and Uttara-Panchala. While Adhichhatra (present-day Bareilly) served as the capital city of Uttara-Panchala, Kampilya was made the capital of Dakshina-Panchala. Formerly a monarchical kingdom, Panchala is believed to have twisted into a republican dominion during the 6th and 5th centuries BC. Kautiliya's 'Arthashastra' also states that Panchala followed the king consul constitution. The kingdom was later annexed by Mauryan Empire and then by the Gupta Empire.

8. Matsya : Located south to the Kuru kingdom and west to river Yamuna, the Matsya kingdom was founded by an Indo-Aryan tribe of Vedic age. Apart from serving as the major water source, Yamuna also alienated Matsya kingdom from the Panchalas. Viratanagara which was named after the kingdom's founder Virata, was Matsya's capital. According to ancient texts, a king named Sujata ruled over Matsya as well as Chedi, which later became a separate kingdom. Though Matsya is mentioned as one of the 'mahajanapadas' in various Buddhist texts, its political authority had greatly dwindled by the time of the Buddha.

9. Chedi : The kingdom of Chedi finds great eminence in the Hindu epic Mahabharata. According to the ancient text, Chedi was ruled by a king named Shishupala, who was an supporter of the kings from Magadha and Kuru. A city named Suktimati has been described as the kingdom's capital. Though the precise location of modern-day Suktimati has not been figured out yet, prominent historians like F. E. Pargiter and Hem Chandra Raychaudhuri say that the ancient city might have been established near present-day Banda in Uttar Pradesh. An Indian archaeologist named Dilip Kumar Chakrabarti has claimed that the ruins of a historical city near the periphery of Rewa in Madhya Pradesh may unlock additional details pertaining to the kingdom and its capital city.

10. Anga : The earliest references to the people of Anga are made in the 'Atharva Veda,' which describes the Angas as despised people. The 'Jaina Prajnapanana' claims that Angas were surrounded by the earliest groups of Aryan people. Over a period of time, the kingdom of Anga became a great center of trade, attracting merchants from the neighboring kingdoms. Anga and its rival Magadha were estranged by river Champa, which served as the main water source for both the kingdoms. Anga was eventually annexed by Magadha in King Bimbisara's one and only conquest.

11. Avanti: Post Mahavira and Buddha, the kingdom of Avanti was considered as one of the four great monarchies along with Kosala, Magadha, and Vatsa. Apart from serving as the kingdom's principal source of water, river Narmada also separated Avanti into two parts – North Avanti and South Avanti.

However, North and South Avanti were integrated at the time of Buddha and Mahavira, during which Ujjaini served as the common capital of the integrated kingdom. Avanti was a great center of Buddhism. When King Shishunaga defeated Nandivardhana, Avanti became a part of Magadha.

12. Vatsa : Vatsa or Vamsa, which was situated near the present-day Allahabad in Uttar Pradesh, thrived under a monarchical form of government. King Udayana of the 7th century BCE ruled Vatsa with Kausambi as its capital. Though Udayana initially contrasting the teachings of the Buddha, he became a follower of Buddha later in his life and even made Buddhism as the state religion of Kausambi. Vatsa's capital city attracted a number of prosperous merchants, who made Kausambi their home. Kausambi was also a prominent Centerport of passengers and goods, coming in from the south and north-west.

13. Assaka: The Kingdom of Assaka was positioned in southern India. Apart from serving as the kingdom's principal foundation of water, river Godavari separated Assaka from Mulaka, which was also recognized as Alaka. It is said that Mulaka was once a part of Assaka. According to Buddhist texts, King Brahmadatta ruled over Assaka with its capital at Potali Assaka is described as one of the 16 'mahajanapadas' in an ancient Buddhist text known as 'Anguttara Nikaya.'

14. Surasena

The kingdom of Surasena was situated to the west of river Yamuna and to the east of Matsya kingdom. Surasena played an imperative role in propagating Buddhism as the king of Surasena, Avantiputra, was among the earliest known chief disciples of Buddha. During the time of Megasthenes, Mathura, the capital of Surasena, was known as a city where worshipping Krishna was considered outstanding The kingdom of Surasena, which once flourished, was later annexed by the Magadhan Empire.

15. Vajji : Vajji was one of the most prominent 'mahajanapadas' of ancient India. Vajji finds declare in the Jaina text 'Bhagavati Sutra' and in Buddhist texts like 'Anguttara Nikaya.' Vajji was located towards the north of the river Ganges and was bound by river Gandaki in the west. Apart from plateful as Vajji's chief source of water, river Gandaki is believed to have played a key role in separating Vajji from Malla and Kosala as well. Apart from Vaishali, which was its capital city, Vajji also housed popular ancient cities like Hatthigama, Bhoganagara, and Kundapura.

16. Kashi : Ancient Kashi was bound by river Varuna in the north and river Assi in the south. The Kingdom of Kashi, which had its capital at Varanasi, was the most imposing among mahajanapadas before the time of the Buddha. Several ancient texts speak highly of Kashi, which was one of the most affluent kingdoms during its glory days Kashi was in steady argument with kingdoms of Kosala, Magadha, and Anga, which were trying to annex Kashi. although Kosala was once defeated by Kashi, it was later annexed by Kosala under the rule of King Kansa, who ruled at the time of Buddha.

ADMINISTRATIVE SYSTEM OF MAHAJANAPADAS : The Mahajanapadas were frequently monarchical kingdoms anywhere dynastic kings with complete powers and a regular army ruled over a defined region called *Janapada* However some of them were republics known as *Gana* or *Ganasanghas* While there was a meditation of monarchies on the Gangetic plain, the republics were scattered in the foothills of the Himalayas and north-western India. By the time of the sixth century BC, Panini mentions as many as 22 different *janapadas*. The early Buddhist and Jain literature sheds a light on the picture of the *Mahajanpada* of the time. They present a list of sixteen Mahajanapadas It is probable that about the sixth century BC, the entire of the Indian subcontinent from Gandhara in modern Afghanistan to the limitations of Bengal was parceled out around among sixteen principal states. Many of the *Janapadas* of the early period developed into Mahajanapadas through this time. Some trendy Mahajanapadas were **Anga, Magadha, Kashi, Kosala, Vajji, Malla, Chedi, Vatsa, Kuru, Panchala, Matsya, Surasena, Asmaka, Avanti, Gandhara and Kambhoja**

Lichachavis, Mallas,, Shakyas, Vajji were some of the important republics. Evidence as to the functions of administration by kings and their officials can be known when we take into account the information gleaned from the Upanishads, the Buddhist canon, the Jataka tradition, or the Dharmasutras literature. These texts supply a picture of the political life of that period. All the writers on polity agree that in order to carry on governance successfully, the state should build up efficient administrative machinery with a king or chiefs at the top assisted by a number of officials. To defray the expenses of administration an elaborate system of taxation was devised. The most distinctive attribute of the polity of this time was that commonly monarchies and republics used to function on the model of a benefit state. Their governance obeys the rule of *Dharma*. Rightful behavior of duties, in the matter of public administration and collection absorption

THE ERA OF DEMOCRATIC ENLIGHTENMENT

After centuries of monarchies and autocracies, the Age of Enlightenment brought forth a resurgence of democratic ideals. Thinkers like John Locke and Montesquieu championed the principles of individual rights, separation of powers, and the social contract, laying the intellectual foundation for modern democracies. The American Revolution 1775–1783 and the subsequent drafting of the United States Constitution reflected the influence of Enlightenment ideals, shaping a constitutional democracy that blended representative and participatory elements.

INTENSIFYING SUFFRAGE: The 19th and early 20th centuries witnessed significant strides in expanding suffrage rights. Movements for women’s suffrage, civil rights, and the abolition of property requirements aimed to make democracy more inclusive and representative. The suffragette movements in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, such as the women’s suffrage movement in the United States and the suffragette campaigns in the UK, resulted in significant advancements in gender equality and expanded political participation.

DEMOCRACY IN ANCIENT INDIA: The Rig Veda is so faithful to democratic philosophy and principles that it has made democracy a deity and aptly called it Samjnana. The term Samjnana means the collective realization of the people, the national mind to which the personality mind is to pay its homage as the source from which it derives its potency. The hymn addressed to Samjnana (in Rig Veda) called upon the people to gather in their assembly (Samgachchaddhvam) and speak there in one voice Samvadaddhvam in a union of minds (Sammanah), of hearts (Samachittam), of policy (Samanmantrah), and of hopes and aspirations (akuti). Thus, democracy was taken to depend upon the ‘inner unity’ of its citizens and their emotional integration. The democratic principle was at work in different spheres of the public life political, social and cultural. The democratic tradition of the Vedic era governed the entire growth of Indian polity through the ages. Even where there was monarchy; it was a limited or constitutional monarchy, so that the pattern of monarchy remained fundamentally democratic. It was based on decentralization and local autonomy. The people formed the following appropriate associations and groups to exercise their rights in self-government in an ascending order: kula (clan), jati (caste), sreni (guild), puga or pura (village community) and janapada (state). Each group had its own rules and regulations and was working for democracy at its respective stratum of self-government. Some of the janapadas in ancient India were republican in form and some had monarchical organisation. But each of them often had an assembly the precursor of the modern parliament—which was attended by the high and the low together with a view to taking decisions about the affairs of the state. R.K. Mukherjee has remarked: “Side by side with the monarchy, there also developed the regular republican type of polity of which glimpses are given in different literary texts—Brahmanical, Buddhist and Jain.” The Mahabharata has also mentioned some republics called Samghatagana.

Five Republican Unions were called: Andhakas, Vrishnis, Yadavas, Kukuras and Bhojas which constituted a Sangha or Union, with Sangha Mukhya as Union President. Similarly, in the Mahabharata, there is a reference to Ganas (republics) being governed by their councils of leaders called Gana-Mukhyas. All these Ganas (republics) had an extremely democratic constitution. Each had its own assembly (parishad). The Jain and the Buddhist texts have also referred to many previous republics and some republican confederations like Vajji (Vriji) consisting of nine Mallakis, nine Lichhavis and eighteen Gana Rajyas of Kashi-Koshal and other states. It has been mentioned that the death of Mahavira was condoled with a funeral enlightenment arranged by 36 republics of this Vriji Confederation. The Lichhavis were well-known republics of those times and were governed by the council of 7,707 Rajas, who were constitutional monarchs. The Sakha republic was famous for giving the Buddha to the world. Nearly 80,000 households constituted the 'republic' which had a parliament of 500 members with a President or Raja. Some of the famous republics of the Buddhist era were: Vaisali, Pava, Mithila and so on. While the assembly served as a legislative body, there were executive and judicial functionaries of various sorts to implement their decisions. A single chief was elected as office-holder presiding over the assembly/state. He bore the title of Raja. It is said that in ancient India, the people led a democratic way of living although political democracy did not exist in its full form. Incidentally, monarchy was also popular. After the sixth century, democratic organizations started declining. Kings and monarchs often remained engaged in wars. Since there was no strong monarch to uphold the solidarity and unity of the country, consequently a large number of principalities sprang up throughout the country. From the eighth century onwards, the Mohammedans launched their invasions till they established their rule in the twelfth century. The Muslim rulers were autocratic. The British rule also was against democracy. It was the Government of India Act, 1935 that laid the foundation stone of democratic rule in India. The Congress remained in power only for two years—from 1935 to 1937. From 1940 to 1945, the British government was preoccupied with the World War II. The efforts for giving political freedom to India started from 1946 till it became free in August 1947. The Constitution of free India accepted democracy as the basis of ruling the country.

DEMOCRACY IN MODERN INDIA:

1. That every individual has his potentialities, worth, and dignity;
2. That everyone has the capacity to learn and manage his life with others;
3. That an individual must abide by the decisions of the majority;
4. That every individual should have a part in making decisions;
5. That the control and way of democratic exploit lies in the situation and not external it.
6. That the process of living is interactive and that all individuals work towards commonly recognized ends; and
7. That democracy rests on individual chance as well as individual responsibility.

After independence, India decided to have democratic political system. This system is characterized by three elements: one, there is a high degree of autonomy; two, economic agents and religious organizations are free from political interference and three competition between various orders does not endanger amalgamation but helps it. Some people maintain that Indira Gandhi's government of 16 years—between January 1966 and October 1984 (minus three years of Morarji Desai and Charan Singh regimes) was not democratic but an demanding regime which had three characteristics:

(Sources by internet)

CHALLENGES AND TRIUMPHS OF THE 20TH CENTURY: The 20th century brought both triumphs and challenges for democracy. World Wars I and II highlighted the importance of democratic values in the face of totalitarianism. However, the Cold War also saw the ideological struggle between democratic and communist systems. The establishment of the United Nations in 1945 aimed to promote international cooperation and prevent conflicts, underscoring a commitment to democratic principles on a global scale.

DIGITAL AGE AND THE INFORMATION REVOLUTION: The advent of the digital age has transformed the way democracies function. The internet and social media have provided extraordinary avenues for citizen engagement and activism. However, concerns about misinformation and the manipulation of public opinion have emerged as new challenges. The Arab Spring 2010–2012 demonstrated the power of social media in mobilizing citizens for political change, yet it also tinted the complexities and reservations of democratization in the digital period. The evolution of democracy from Ancient Greece to modern times reflects an ongoing quest for a system that best serves the interests of the people. As we navigate the challenges of the 21st century, understanding the historical context and lessons of the past can guide us in shaping more robust and inclusive democratic societies. The journey of democracy is far from complete, and its continued evolution will undoubtedly shape the future of governance for generations to come.

CONSTITUTIONAL DEMOCRACY IN INDIA: Constitutional democracy is a form of government where the Constitution serves as the supreme law of the land, exactness the powers and limitations of the government. This system ensures that power is circulated consistently among special branches of government, preventing any one branch from becoming too powerful. In a constitutional democracy, the government derives its authority from the permission of the people, who have the power to elect their representatives. The Constitution protects individual rights and freedoms, such as freedom of speech, freedom of the press, and freedom of religion.

IMPORTANT TENETS OF CONSTITUTIONAL DEMOCRACY:

1. Rule of Law: Everyone is subject to the law, and no one is above the law.

2. Separation of Powers: Power is divided among different branches of government, such as the legislative, executive, and judiciary.
3. Protection of Minority Rights: The rights of minorities are protected, and they are not subject to the whims of the majority.
4. Free and Fair Elections: Elections are held regularly and the process is visible and flaxen

MERITS OF CONSTITUTIONAL DEMOCRACY:

1. Peaceful Transfer of Power: The government can change softly all the way through elections.
2. Defense of Individual Rights: The Constitution protects individual rights and freedoms.
3. Good Governance: The government is responsible to the people, and there are checks and balances in place to stay away from exploitation of power.
4. equal opportunity promotion
5. protects the rights of people
6. an absence of power monopoly
7. Democracy improves the quality of decision making,
8. Democracy enhances the dignity of citizens
9. Poor and least educated have the same status as the rich and educated

DEMERITS OF CONSTITUTIONAL DEMOCRACY:

1. Delay in Decision-Making: The process of decision-making can be slowing suitable to the separation of powers.
2. Corruption: Corruption can still survive in a constitutional democracy if there are loopholes in the scheme
3. Minority Rights: The rights of minorities can still be in jeopardy if the majority does not admiration their rights.
4. It costs too much to run.
5. While minor opinions are occasionally ignored, majority opinions are typically imposed
On people.

CONCLUSION: Democracy is the greatest government system in the world. Among the world 195 of Countries 93% of the Nations adopted and follow direct or indirect system of the Democracy. India is one of the largest and highest populations (nearly 147 cr. People) and constitutional parliamentary system of the government. we will see the democratic principles of the government earliest centuries like BC and AC. Growth and revelation of the democracy in the world Ancient Greek, and Indian Mahajanapadas and other civilization era of the world. Administration system also growth with Ancient civilization and Mahajanapadas. After Glorious Revolution of the England (1688) Modern democratic system enter in to the world. There after American Revolution (1773-1776) and France Revolution (1787) and also other countries People awareness regarding the Democratic system of the Government is growing on like al world countries. Countries with rule of law. Presently the best Government system in world.

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MODI GOVERNMENT AND CENTRE-STATE RELATIONS: A FEDERAL BALANCING IN CONTEMPORARY INDIA

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Abstract

The dynamics of Centre-State relations in India have always been pivotal in shaping the country's federal structure, particularly under the leadership of Prime Minister Narendra Modi. Since assuming office in 2014, the Modi government has undertaken several measures that have significantly influenced the contours of Indian federalism. This abstract examines the evolving nature of Centre-State relations during the Modi era, highlighting the dual tendencies of cooperative and confrontational federalism. While initiatives such as the formation of NITI Aayog, the implementation of the Goods and Services Tax (GST), and increased fiscal devolution reflect a shift toward cooperative federalism, several issues raise concerns about growing centralization of power. The use of central agencies, imposition of President's Rule, and interventions in opposition-ruled states have sparked debates over the autonomy of states and the erosion of federal principles. Additionally, the handling of crucial areas such as health, agriculture, and internal security—especially during the COVID-19 pandemic and farmers' protests—further exposed tensions in Centre-State coordination. Despite constitutional safeguards, the balance of power has often tilted in favor of the Centre, leading to charges of asymmetrical federalism. However, the federal fabric continues to adapt through judicial interventions, political negotiations, and civil society activism. This abstract underscores the need for a more inclusive and institutionalized framework of intergovernmental relations that honors both the unity and diversity of India's polity. In essence, the Modi government's tenure marks a critical phase in the ongoing negotiation between central authority and regional autonomy within India's democratic federation.

Key Words: Centre-State relations, cooperative federalism, Government, Commission Election

Introduction

The Indian federal structure, as enshrined in the Constitution, creates a union of states that shares power between the Centre and the states. Since Narendra Modi assumed office in 2014, the Centre-State relationship has witnessed significant transformation. While some argue that the Modi government has promoted cooperative federalism through initiatives like the Goods and Services Tax (GST) and NITI Aayog, critics point to increasing centralization and the marginalization of regional autonomy. This research investigates the central tendencies, institutional reforms, political strategies, and fiscal patterns that have defined Modi-era federalism. It contextualizes the debate in the broader historical and constitutional framework of Indian federalism.

Constitutional Basis of Centre-State Relations

The Indian Constitution provides a quasi-federal structure where the Centre enjoys more power than the states. Articles 245 to 263 define the legislative, administrative, and financial relationships between the Union and the states.

- Legislative Powers: Defined in the Seventh Schedule, with three lists: Union, State, and Concurrent. The Parliament has overriding powers in the Concurrent List.
- Administrative Relations: The Centre can give directions to states for compliance with Union laws (Article 256).
- Financial Relations: The Centre collects the majority of revenues and shares them with states through Finance Commissions.

The Constitution also provides mechanisms like the Inter-State Council (Article 263) and the Zonal Councils to resolve disputes and promote coordination.

Modi Government's Vision of Federalism

Since coming to power, the Modi government emphasized "cooperative federalism" and later "competitive federalism." These concepts promoted collaboration and performance-based competition among states. NITI Aayog: Replacing the Planning Commission in 2015, NITI Aayog aimed to foster a more participative approach with states. Team India Approach: Promoted equal participation of states in national policymaking.

However, this vision has often been critiqued for being symbolic rather than substantial.

Fiscal Federalism: GST and Finance Commissions

The implementation of the Goods and Services Tax (GST) in 2017 was a landmark reform. While it aimed to unify the tax structure, it also led to new tensions:

GST Council: Though a collaborative platform, states often felt sidelined. Compensation Issues: The Centre's delay in compensating states for revenue losses during COVID-19 worsened trust. Finance Commission Recommendations: The 15th Finance Commission recommended more conditional grants, which many states viewed as a way for the Centre to influence state priorities.

Fiscal centralization has increased, with states relying heavily on central transfers and grants-in-aid.

Political Tensions and Partisan Federalism

The Modi government has faced allegations of using central institutions and agencies to undermine opposition-led states.

- Use of Governors: States like Maharashtra, West Bengal, and Tamil Nadu have accused governors of acting as agents of the Centre.
- CBI and ED Investigations: Several non-BJP state leaders have been targeted by central agencies, raising concerns over political misuse.
- Article 356: Though sparingly used, fears of its misuse persist in politically volatile situations.

These developments have led to what some scholars term "partisan federalism."

Cooperative vs Competitive Federalism: A Policy Review

Federalism in India has undergone significant transformation, especially in the post-1990 economic liberalization phase and more prominently under recent governments. Cooperative federalism emphasizes partnership and collaboration between the Centre and States to achieve common national goals. Initiatives such as the replacement of the Planning Commission with NITI Aayog, implementation of Goods and Services Tax (GST), and fiscal decentralization reflect attempts at building a consensus-driven model of governance. In this model, states are seen as stakeholders in national development, with greater involvement in policy planning and execution.

In contrast, competitive federalism encourages states to compete with one another to attract investment, improve service delivery, and foster innovation. This approach, emphasized under the Modi government, promotes healthy rivalry through mechanisms like ranking of states on ease of doing business, education outcomes, and health indices. It aims to increase efficiency and accountability by fostering competition.

However, challenges persist. Critics argue that competitive federalism may deepen regional disparities, while cooperative efforts often face issues of unequal power distribution. Thus, a balanced interplay of both models is essential. India's federal trajectory demands a blend of cooperation and competition to ensure inclusive, efficient, and equitable development. for example;

- ❖ Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, PM-Kisan, Ayushman Bharat: While these schemes were implemented nationwide, states had limited say in design and implementation.
- ❖ Aspirational Districts Programme: Promoted competition among states but often lacked input from state governments.
- ❖ One Nation, One Ration Card: Aimed at portability of benefits, but faced resistance from states citing operational challenges.
- ❖ While the Centre positioned itself as a facilitator, many states argued they were reduced to mere implementers.

Regional Autonomy and Identity Politics

The Modi government era has witnessed a complex interplay between regional autonomy and identity politics in India. While the Indian Constitution guarantees a quasi-federal structure with significant powers to the states, the period since 2014 has seen increased centralization, often leading to tensions between the Centre and states, particularly those ruled by opposition parties. The Modi government's emphasis on "One Nation, One Tax" (GST), One Nation, One Ration Card, and uniform welfare schemes has raised concerns over the dilution of regional autonomy.

At the same time, identity politics rooted in language, ethnicity, culture, and regional pride has intensified. In states like Tamil Nadu, West Bengal, and Punjab, regional parties have asserted their distinct cultural and linguistic identities to resist perceived homogenization by the Centre. The abrogation of Article 370 in Jammu & Kashmir in 2019, which revoked its special autonomous status, marked a significant shift in Centre-State relations, leading to a nationwide debate on federalism and regional rights.

Policies such as the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) also triggered identity-based protests in Assam and other northeastern states, where concerns about cultural preservation and indigenous rights were foregrounded. While the Modi government has promoted national integration and development through central schemes, critics argue that it has often sidelined regional aspirations and democratic consultations.

Overall, the era has highlighted a growing assertion of regional identities in response to centralizing tendencies, emphasizing the need for a more balanced approach that respects diversity while promoting national unity.

Recommendations for Strengthening Federalism

1. Institutional Reforms: Revive Inter-State Council, empower Zonal Councils, and enhance NITI Aayog's participative role.
2. Clarify Governor's Role: Through constitutional amendment or detailed guidelines.
3. Transparent Use of Agencies: Ensure accountability in the functioning of ED, CBI, and other bodies.
4. Greater Fiscal Autonomy: Implement Finance Commission recommendations in letter and spirit.
5. Respect Regional Diversity: Avoid imposing a uniform national culture or language.
6. Judicial Oversight: Encourage timely resolution of Centre-State disputes through dedicated benches.

Conclusion

The Modi government's tenure has redefined the contours of Centre-State relations in India. While rhetorically committed to cooperative federalism, the Centre's actions often reflect a centralizing impulse. The balance between national integration and regional autonomy remains delicate.

Strengthening institutions, fostering genuine dialogue, and respecting the constitutional spirit of federalism are essential to sustaining India's unity in diversity.

As India moves toward becoming a \$5 trillion economy, robust and equitable Centre-State relations will be vital for inclusive and sustainable growth. The future of Indian federalism depends on how well it adapts to emerging challenges without compromising its democratic ethos.

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ECONOMIC AND SOCIO INFRASTRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TRIBAL FARMERS IN KARNATAKA A CASE STUDY OF CHAMARAJANAGARA DISTRICT

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India has the largest concentration of tribal population. The tribes are the aboriginal people of the land who are believed to be the earliest settlers in the original inhabitants. The ancient and medieval sources of the information including the Vedic and the Epic literature mention various tribes like the Soligas, Bharatas, the Bhils, the Kollas, the Kirtars, the Kinnars, the Kiris, the Matsyas, the Nisadas and the Banars.

Majority of the scheduled tribes live in isolated or partially isolated regions of hills and forests and in many ways their style of life is distinct from that of the general society. Demographically, the scheduled tribes are concentrated in certain regions of the State. The majority of tribal population inhabits the isolated hilly areas which are often inaccessible. Scheduled tribes are especially in the rural areas still identified with extreme poverty, illiteracy, under-nutrition and mal-nutrition, forced migration due to lack of employment particularly in agricultural sector.

The main socio-economic problems effective the bulk of the tribal population are chronic indebtedness, landlessness, lack of education, forced labour, lack of employment and low wages and the problem of child labour. In the above circumstances the present study is mainly concentrated to know the socio-economic and infrastructural characteristics of scheduled tribes in a, drought prone district of chamarajanagara of Karnataka.

While analyzing the socio-economic and infrastructural characteristics of tribal farmers at micro-level, several parameters are taken for the analysis. For this purpose sample villages were selected on the basis of developed and backward villages. The educational status, economic conditions of the sample households and size of the family of the Scheduled Tribes are the major parameters for the present study.

Family Size of the tribal Households

Generally the family size among Scheduled Tribe population will be high due to lack of awareness about family planning, illiteracy, health carrying system etc. Of the total large family size of Scheduled Tribe holdings, 95 per cent are illiterates and 55 per cent belongs to poor economic category. It shows that illiteracy is the main cause for larger family size in the down-trodden tribal people in Chamarajanagara district of Karnataka.

A moderate family size with 4 to 6 persons is found in 55 per cent of the total sample size. The same family size with 1 to 3 persons is accounted for 21 per cent of the total sample size. It reveals that the literacy and economic status have some significant impact on small family size among the tribals in the district.

The medium to large family size is found in three-fourths of the total sample size which confirms the general hypothesis that large family sizes are not uncommon among the Scheduled Tribe holdings. It manifests that the illiteracy and economic backwardness still prevails a significant effect on family size of the tribals. From the personal investigation with the sample holdings, it is noticed that the traditional sentiment i.e., more persons in a family earn more wages and also stand for security for themselves is still in vogue in some of the tribal families in rural Andhra Pradesh.

Dwelling, Drinking Water, Electricity and Sanitary facilities in Tribal Villages: From the sample size, it is found that all the holdings are possessed housing facility except one. But the house type varied from roof cover (RC) to brick wall with thatched houses, mud wall with thatched houses and huts. Majority of house types are found with RC (85.1%) which are being provided by Government Housing Scheme for poor followed by huts 4.1 per cent and mud wall with thatched houses 3.2 per cent. All the houses are well provided with protective drinking water facility as well as electricity.

With regard to drainage and sanitary facilities, as is expected in rural areas, there is no proper drainage system and sanitation in any of the sample holdings. Due to lack of these facilities environment of the surroundings of the houses are seemed to be poor in outlook.

Transport Facilities for Tribals:

From the sample data it is noticed that 67.3 per cent of the total sample size don't have any mode of owned transport vehicles for their local movement. The sample holdings who do not have any transport vehicles for their local movement are largely from backward villages and poor economic status.

The tribal households those are having owned transport vehicles are numbered to 43 holdings, out of which, 16 holdings belonged to non-poor category and 27 holdings belonged to poor economic category. The types of vehicle for internal transport used by the holdings are bicycle, moped and scooter. Out of all the vehicles, bicycle is the cheapest mode of transport which is being used by 70 per cent of tribal holdings. Scooters are being used by 18.5 per cent of sample holdings. The use of vehicles for internal transport is found more in tribal holdings comparatively with the other weaker sections in the sample villages.

The communication facilities like Radio, Tape Recorder and Television are available in 31 sample holdings. Out of 31 holdings having communication facilities, 20 holdings belonged to non-poor economic category and remaining 11 holdings belonged to poor economic status. It is very clear that economic status is the significant criterion for having owned communication facilities.

Among the various means of communication and recreation facilities, radio is the most popular communication facility being possessed by 69 per cent of the total sample holdings. Because of its low price it is being owned by majority of sample holdings. The next important type is tape recorder which is being owned by 27.5 per cent. Since the cost of television is very high, it cannot be afforded by large number of tribal holdings in the district.

Occupational Structure of Tribals:

It is pertinent to state that agriculture is the predominant occupation of tribal population, which is evident from the fact that out of 70 total sample holdings, 50 sample holdings are found to be engaged in agriculture. So it shows that agriculture is the main source of livelihood for tribal population in Chamarajanagara district.

Nature of Agricultural Ownership and Size of Land Holdings: Out of the total sample size of 70 holdings, the predominant nature of holdings is agricultural labourers numbered to 61 sample holdings. It is followed by owner cultivators with 39 holdings. Tenant cultivators are very less in number among the tribals in sample villages of the district.

The number of sample holdings with the possession of agricultural land is found to be 41 holdings. The remaining sample holdings are landless. It reveals that tribal population significantly is found to be less agricultural land in the district. Out of total land holdings with agricultural land, 28 holdings are found to be completely dry land holdings and it followed by six holdings found with both wet and dry land holdings and seven holdings are found with wet land. It clearly shows that the

agricultural land holdings of tribal cultivators are by and large dry land holdings without irrigation facility and of intensive cultivation.

Sources of Irrigation

The two sources of irrigation namely tank and well irrigations are noticed in[^] irrigating the land holdings of tribals. Of the available two types of irrigation well is the major source providing irrigation water to the tribal holdings. The next important source of irrigation is tank irrigation during the good monsoon years in the district.

Mode of Cultivation

As would be expected in the downtrodden poor agriculturists especially tribal farmers, the mode of cultivation is traditional with wooden plough and bullocks, of the 41 land holdings using different modes of cultivation, wooden plough with bullocks is predominant mode of cultivating land by 68.9 per cent of the sample holdings. The second important and primitive mode of cultivation which is still being done by tribals is wooden plough with buffaloes. This type of cultivation has been accounted by 22.8 per cent of tribal farmers in the sample villages. It is interesting to state that all the scheduled tribe population who are cultivating the land are still being used wooden ploughs with buffaloes.

Use of Manures, Pesticides and High Yielding Varieties: Using both cow-dung and chemical fertilizers is the general practice of manuring the fields by sample tribal land holdings. This type of manure and practice is found in all the sample holdings. Application of chemical fertilizers alone to the fields is found in tribal owner type of cultivation. Use of green manure is noticed in ten land holdings belonged to tribal population. From this analysis, it is very clear that use of both cow dung and¹ fertilizers is a common practice of small farmers belongs to tribal community in the district.

With regard to application of pesticides 36 sample tribal land holdings are using pesticides for the control of crop diseases. It is a good sign indeed. But it is paradoxical to say that the practice of hybrid cultivation is very insignificant among tribal farmers which is evident from the fact that only 12 land holdings have stated the practice of hybrid cultivation and rest of the land holdings are still cultivating the agricultural land with traditional seeds.

Farm Credit among the Tribal Farmers

Credit agencies can play an important role in the provision of farm capital to the farmers especially the small and marginal farmers. In order to adopt modern technology and possibly the development of land and water resources, there are various sources of getting farm credit namely co-operative credit societies, co-operative agricultural development banks, nationalized banks, private banks, and or private money lenders. Nearly 55 per cent of tribal land holdings are depending upon agricultural loans from banks. About 60 per cent of illiterate farmers are depending more upon institutional credit while it is very low (17.1%) in the case of literate farmers. In respect of economic status nearly 70 per cent of non-poor and while 36 per cent of poor farmers depending upon institutional credit.

It is very interesting to state that all the sample holdings have expressed that they did not get the agricultural loans from the banks at right time for carrying prerequisite agricultural operations. If they don't get the farm credit at right time to carry out the necessary agricultural operations that farm credit will not be much useful for betterment of agricultural production.

Out of the indebted landholdings, 80.8 per cent of tribal land holdings have taken farm credit from private money lenders at high interest rate by giving promissory deed. In contrast only 40 per cent of tribal land holdings have taken loan from the banks by putting their land deed or jewellery.

It reveals that private money lenders are the major source of getting farm credit to the poor tribal land holdings in the drought prone Chamarajanagara district. Though the interest rate is very high in the case of private money lenders the farmers will get the credit at right time for carrying the necessary agricultural operations. Whereas in the case of getting institutional, the farmers have been facing several problems in order to get the loan amount and also at right time.

Conclusions

The tribal families in rural areas are mainly depending on agricultural sector as agriculturists or as agricultural laborers. The socio-economic conditions of tribals are low. The awareness of family planning operations are poor among the tribals and for that reason the size of the family of tribal holdings is large comparatively with other downtrodden sections in drought prone district of Chamarajanagara.

The transport and communication facilities available for tribal households are not satisfactory. For the purpose of medical facilities, the tribal people have been depending on local untrained doctors or rural ayurvedic doctors. The landholding sizes among the tribals are very small. The use of fertilizers and pesticides are not in productive economic status.

Though they are availing various developmental schemes their economic conditions are still poor. This is mainly because of illiteracy and ignorance among the tribals/ The availability of credit facilities for agricultural operations is not satisfactory. The banking agencies are not providing credit facilities at right time and the amount sanctioned by these institutional agencies is not sufficient for their agricultural operations.

The government should, provide, proper educational facilities to tribals in rural areas along with medical services. Proper training programmes for various self employment programmes and agricultural extension services are necessary to the tribals. Timely sanction of loans at low rate of interest from the institutional agencies increase the productivity of agriculture and also it helps to increase the socio-economic status among the tribals in rural areas.

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CONSTITUTIONAL MORALITY AND DEMOCRATIC PRACTICE IN INDIA**T Sunil¹ & Shreedhar Barki^{1*}**

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Abstract

This article examines the challenges faced by Indian democracy in fostering constitutional morality and a democratic ethos among its citizens. Despite 77 years of democratic governance, India continues to grapple with the inculcation of democratic principles and constitutional morality within its population. This study analyzes the perspectives of pre- and post-independence scholars on the development of democratic practices in India. Key arguments emphasize that democracy was externally imposed rather than internally developed and that Indian society remains deeply entrenched in caste and community identities rather than individual rights. It examines how political parties have failed to adequately cultivate democratic values, instead frequently prioritizing ideological and communal interests over national welfare. This study posits that this ideological fragmentation and disregard of democratic principles by political actors poses a significant threat to India's democratic system. The persistence of these challenges, from the concerns of constitutional framers to contemporary thinkers, underscores the ongoing struggle to cultivate a truly democratic ethos in India.

Key words: Constitutional Morality, Democratic Ethos, Individual Liberty, Group Rights, Political Parties

Introduction

Democracy is widely regarded as the optimal form of governance, and India has adopted it since its independence. The proper functioning and success of liberal democracy in any nation depends upon several key factors: individual liberty, equality, fraternity (mutual understanding), and adherence to the rules, regulations, and principles enshrined in the constitution. Thus, these principles should be cultivated within a population. During constitutional assembly debates, the framers emphasized the importance of constitutional morality, which they deemed essential for the success and sustainability of liberal democracy. Moreover, they observed that the Indian population was not yet fully receptive to the principles of liberal democracy. They remained optimistic about a future India in which democratic institutions would help cultivate democratic principles and constitutional morality among its citizens. However, their observations remain relevant, and their optimistic vision has not yet been fully realized, as evidenced by contemporary discourse on constitutional morality and democratic practices in India. In light of these considerations, this study aims to present and compare various arguments from scholars across different periods – pre- and post-independence – regarding constitutional morality and democratic practices. The objective is to examine perspectives and ideologies concerning how these concepts are understood and implemented by the Indian population, political leaders, and political parties.

Debates on Indian Democracy and Constitutional Morality

“Democracy emerged in India out of a confrontation with a power imposed from outside rather than an engagement with the contradictions inherent in Indian society. Those contradictions deeply embedded in the Indian society even after adopting democracy” (Beteille 2017, 9-10). During the independence movement, the populace voiced its opposition to British rule and demanded liberation from foreign governance. However, they did not consider the nature of the system that would require post-independence. It was the educated elite who studied at Western universities and introduced democracy to India. The general population residing in the country lacked familiarity with the concepts of

constitution and democratic governance. According to **Ambedkar** "Constitutional morality is not a natural sentiment to Indians, it has to be cultivated. We must realize that our people are yet to learn it. Democracy in India is only a top dressing on an Indian soil, which is essentially undemocratic" (*Ibid.* 78) Ambedkar's observations remain pertinent to India's contemporary political context. Despite 77 years of democratic governance, the nation continues to face challenges in terms of citizens' adherence to democratic principles. India lacked the prerequisite conditions for democracy. It was incumbent upon the leaders, civil society, and political parties to establish conditions and foster democratic ethos among the general population. The question arises as to whether they have succeeded in cultivating a democratic ethos among the general population of India. This issue is addressed in the latter part of this study.

The stronger the presence of constitutional morality, the less need there is to put everything in black and white (Beteille 2017, 78). This statement resembles Ambedkar's justification of a lengthy and elaborate constitution—"the absence of democratic tradition required the provisions in the constitution to be written out in much greater detail than in the more mature democracies where there was greater consensus on how democratic institutions should function" (*Ibid.*78). Ambedkar considered these countries (French, American, and British) as mature democracies that established democracies by challenging and confronting their internal problems. In such societies, individuals are cognizant of their rights and duties. However, in India, he insists that such maturities must be cultivated among Indians, which they lack. He consistently emphasized the importance of individuals and advocated for their recognition as units of society rather than the community (CAD 2014, XI: 833). Nevertheless, what transpired in post-independent India was that, in the name of identity politics, communities gained more prominence than individuals. Here, the populace consistently demonstrated a greater inclination towards group rights than toward individual rights. Institutions, political parties, and leaders have not endeavored to cultivate liberal democratic principles in the general population. "The basic principles of modern liberal democracy include the idea that the individual is of major importance in society" (Baradat 2012, 69). Indian democratic practices and Indians are insensitive to this principle.

During constitutional debates, the framers expressed concern that, following immediate independence, they would face difficulties in cultivating democratic principles among the general population. This concern was articulated by **B. M. Gupte**: "We must have faith in our principles and faith in the common man. Our infant democracy will, of course, have teething troubles, and its adolescence may be marked by mischievous pranks; but in spite of the initial trouble and occasional lapses, I hope generally and ultimately the commonsense of the common man will triumph" (CAD 2014, XI: 845). He was optimistic about India's future and believed that institutions and other democratic vehicles would cultivate democratic ethos among the general population. However, the constitutional framers' concerns remain unfulfilled, as evidenced in the thoughts of contemporary thinkers.

According to **Beteille**, "Indian society is a society of castes and communities. It was not a society of citizens based on the equal consideration of individuals without regard for caste, creed, or gender. To transform a society of caste and communities into one of citizens would be no easy task" (Beteille 2017, 77). Furthermore, he asserted that regardless of the quality of the constitution, the absence of constitutional morality renders it arbitrary; without some infusion of constitutional morality among legislators, judges, lawyers, ministers, civil servants, writers, and public intellectuals, the constitution becomes a plaything of power brokers (*Ibid.*78). While Gupte's concern was to cultivate a democratic ethos among the general population, but in the current context (Beteille), the discussion centers on

instilling democratic values and constitutional morality among legislators, judges, lawyers, ministers, civil servants, writers, and intellectuals.

Non-conducive conditions for democracy continued in India. Here, the population does not have a sense of individual rights. **Mehta** states that “despite five decades of democratic functioning, it unsuccessful in formation of democratic citizens who has sense of right and wrong; sensitive of social consciences; minimal sense of justice. Indians are insensitive to these aspects. Indians are incapable of performing tasks which upheld democratic practices because Indians lived in cultural inheritance which linked with past injustice. This is where India disliking from creating democratic citizens” (Mehta 2003, 22). Let us compare Mehta’s statement with that of R. V. Dhulekar and T J M Wilson’s statement respectively- “we are going to have village panchayats, which is an extension of democracy to the lowest ground. For some years we had democracy in India, but the common man never felt that he possessed any democracy. As we extend our democracy to the villages and establish the village panchayats, and ask the common man to govern himself, I believe that India will be far better than England or America” (CAD 2014, XI: 826); “the essence of democracy is the effective participation of the individual in the actual government of the country. The greater and more effective the participation of the individual in the government, the greater is the democracy” (*Ibid.*857).

The conditions were not changed. People in India are still ignorant and insensitive to their individual rights; they become active only when their community is in threat or danger. In the process of selecting representatives, individuals do not evaluate candidates based on their qualifications; instead, they choose them solely on the basis of caste and other group affiliations. These voters remain insensitive to discerning what is ethically correct or incorrect, as well as those who possess the capacity to make such distinctions.

Our democratic institutions also failed to cultivate democratic values among citizens. “The politics has become an area where norms exist only in their breach. Democratic mobilization, while it has produced an intense struggle for power, has not delivered millions of citizens from- poverty” (Mehta 2003, 13). Further Mehta states that in India democracy has become ‘hollow shell’ (*Ibid.* 14), which has a body, but no life. India has democracy, but it does not function based on democratic principles. This raises a serious question: can democracy function without democratic principles? According to Mehta, moral crises are the biggest challenge for democracies. Moral consensus is important for the success of democracy. This will guide people to adhere to the rules and regulations of the states. In democracy, mobilizations should take place on a social democratic basis, which has universalistic demands for health, education, welfare, and so on. However, in Indian democracies, people always mock the rules of the states by breaking them. Rather than universal demand, individuals exert pressure on the government on group-specific (caste and community related) issues.

Nehru stated that ‘Our democracy is a tender plant, which has to be nourished’ (Varshney 2013, 25), and it is ironic that the nourishing process continues despite 77 years of democratic governance in independent India. Political parties, civil society, educated youth, experienced intellectual communities, mainstream media, and vast social media domains have not succeeded in educating and cultivating democratic consciousness and values among Indian citizens, which are essential to democracy. According to Varshney, Indian democracy faces challenges in fostering national unity by minimizing religious differences, caste differences, and linguistic divisions (*Ibid.* 31-32), of which the first two differences existed before independence, and the latter resulted from the linguistic states introduced in the democratic system. This indicates that democracy in India has not effectively created public awareness of the concepts of a progressive society and a welfare state. Citizens continue to prioritize

communal and linguistic issues over individual and general societal welfare. This situation exemplifies the paradox of contemporary Indian liberal democracy.

The arguments discussed above include those of constitutional makers: Ambedkar, Nehru, B M Gupte, and R. V. Dhulekar, among others, and contemporary Indian thinkers such as Andre Beteille, Pratap Bhanu Mehta, and Ashutosh Varshney, who have written on Indian democracy and constitutional morality. A key observation of these thinkers' arguments is that constitutional makers' concerns regarding constitutional morality and democratic practices in India have persisted and are reflected in the work of present-day intellectuals. The vision and confidence that constitutional framers held for India's future remain unfulfilled, and present-day thinkers raise concerns similar to those of early Indian thinkers (the mid-20th century).

This indicates that despite seventy-seven years of independence and democratic practices, citizens remain insensitive to democratic ethos. Why are people insensitive to democratic principles and constitutional ethos? In addressing this inquiry, we aim to demonstrate that ideology is one of the factors contributing to the challenges in citizens' commitment to democratic values.

Ideology and Democratic Practice: Role of Political Parties

The aforementioned arguments demonstrate that in India, there is a notable absence of significant concern regarding constitutional values or democratic principles among the population. In a post-independence democratic framework, individual liberty should have assumed paramount importance. However, the prevailing circumstances contradict the fundamental principles of democracy in India. Community interests play a predominant role in political mobilization and policymaking. Political parties, leaders, intellectuals, non-governmental organizations, and civil society serve as the primary vehicles for cultivating a democratic ethos among the general population. Nevertheless, these domains are ideologically divided; each adheres to its own ideological position and often disregards democratic values in pursuit of their objectives.

According to **Ashutosh Varshney**, "a democracy cannot function if the institutional logic of the system is made subservient to the personal ambition or the ideological predilections of political leaders" (Varshney 2013, 59). Political parties, as significant political entities, are obligated to mobilize citizens for matters of general welfare, including education, employment, enhancement of the healthcare sector, and the mitigation of poverty and hunger. These issues represent genuine challenges faced by individuals. Political parties should prioritize these concerns during electoral campaigns and subsequent policy formulations to secure victory. However, parties are not addressing these matters; instead, they are engaging in divisive politics, gravitating towards ideological predispositions to secure electoral success.

Political parties disregard for democratic values poses significant threats to democratic practices. The consequences of ideological fragmentation and the subversion of democratic principles by political parties undermine the foundation of India's democratic system. Our political parties are ideologically divided: Congress adheres to socialism and minority appeasement; Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) adheres to Hindu nationalism; regional parties mobilize people by addressing regional issues that engender heightened sentimentality towards their region and languages; BSP, JDU, RJD, etc., are considered champions of lower castes; and Shiv Sena is known for Hindutva and Marathi regionalism etc. These political parties contend for ideological predilections and mobilize people accordingly. To accumulate support for their concerns, these parties often resort to divisive tactics and populist rhetoric. This approach not only deepens societal rift, but also distracts from pressing national issues that require

unified attention. As a result, the electorate becomes increasingly polarized, making it challenging to foster a cohesive national identity and implement policies that benefit the country as a whole.

Political parties prioritize ends over means, with their primary aim being to acquire or maintain authority. To accomplish this, they consistently mislead and swayed the public, according to their agenda. A recent controversy in Karnataka involves waqf property (October 2024), where it is alleged that farmland was classified as a waqf property. The opposition party, the BJP, portrayed this as a critical issue; however, the same party did not emphasize farmers' suicides or the fair pricing of agricultural produce as pressing concerns. Similarly, mainstream media provided limited coverage of farmers' genuine problems but extensively reported on the waqf issue.

In the same state, the Congress party promised five guaranteed benefits to citizens in its manifesto. After winning the elections, it implemented all associated programs. This was followed by criticism from the political and intellectual spheres. One group commended it as a socialistic principle that assisted impoverished individuals, while others criticized it as unnecessary provisions that ostensibly fostered indolence. It is noteworthy that the Congress Party promised this for electoral success rather than poverty alleviation. When it received criticism, it began projecting it as a socialistic principle on which its ideology was based. Ironically, the political party (BJP) that criticized guaranteed benefits in Karnataka made similar promises in Jammu and Kashmir- 'Maa Samman Yojana' promises to provide 18,000 annually to senior most woman in family, which is similar to 'Gruha Lakshmi' guarantee scheme of Karnataka. (Refer: Karnataka Assembly Election Manifesto -2023 and Sankalp Patra 2024, BJP manifesto, Jammu and Kashmir).

Political parties consistently manipulate the electorate during elections, attracting public attention by appealing manifestos and promises. This strategy diverts the public focus from genuine day-to-day problems, encouraging votes in favor of political parties that promised attractive promises, provisions, increased reservation quotas, and internal reservation implementation etc.

The Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), currently in an incumbent position, is known for its Hindutva politics. It gained prominence through the demolition of the Babri Masjid and its promise to construct a Ram temple on the disputed land in Ayodhya. In 2014, the BJP attained power at the central level with a clear majority as well as in numerous state assembly elections. The party has proposed policies such as the Uniform Civil Code, prohibition of cow slaughter, ban on hijabs (in Karnataka), and the Waqf Amendment Bill 2024. These initiatives of the BJP are not aligned with the principles of establishing a welfare state. Rather, they are manifestations of the party's ideology, which is oriented towards Hindu nationalism. To this end, the BJP targets Muslims as a means of consolidating and mobilizing individuals from the Hindu community. The BJP's policies and actions have significantly affected India's democratic practices. The prioritization of Hindu nationalism over addressing the genuine day-to-day problems faced by the population has significant implications. These issues are likely to play a prominent role in public discourse and potentially lead to new challenges such as communal violence. The party's approach has polarized the electorate, potentially marginalizing minority groups. This strategy challenges the fundamental tenets of inclusive democracy, raising concerns about equal representation and the protection of diverse religious and cultural identities within the nation's democratic framework.

From independence to the present, political parties have engaged in these practices, impeding the functioning of the fundamental principles of liberal democracy. Political parties are not working in favor of individual interests and general welfare; most of them are oriented towards group rights, attractive

promises, and ideological predilections. Parties have consistently prioritized electoral victory over the cultivation of constitutional morality and democratic principles among citizens.

Conclusion:

This study demonstrates an enduring discrepancy between the ideals of India's constitution and the actual implementation of its democracy. Even after 77 years of democratic rule, India still struggles to instill constitutional morality and democratic values in its population. The issues raised by early thinkers such as Ambedkar and Gupte continue to be pertinent today, as noted by modern scholars. This study identifies several crucial factors that contribute to this ongoing challenge. First, democracy in India was imposed from -outside rather than evolving from internal social conflicts, resulting in a lack of deeply ingrained democratic customs. Second, Indian society remains firmly rooted in caste and community identities, often emphasizing group rights over individual freedoms. Third, political parties and their ideologies have significantly influenced the development of citizens, who are frequently indifferent to constitutional morality and fundamental democratic principles. This article emphasizes the necessity of a coordinated effort to promote democratic values and constitutional awareness across all societal segments, including lawmakers, government officials, and the general population. It also advocates a transition from identity-based politics to a more inclusive, right-centered democratic practice. Ultimately, the study suggests that fostering constitutional morality and a democratic ethos remains an ongoing challenge for India, requiring continued dedication from all participants in the democratic process.

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RELEVANCE OF DR. BHIMRAO AMBEDKAR'S IDEAS ON SOCIAL JUSTICE IN MODERN INDIA: A SOCIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The paper is an attempt to explore the concept of social justice and empowerment in the views of Dr. Ambedkar's. According to him, a justice means a good working social order whose actions, instructions, laws and moral rules are geared to promote the greatest possible common good. Common good is the basic idea of Dr. Ambedkar's concept of social justice. A deep study of the constitution as a whole reveals the quest of Dr. Ambedkar for social revolution for the reconstruction of an egalitarian and casteless society. The Indian constitution empowers the society that state to make special provisions for guaranteeing equality, elimination of discrimination on the grounds of caste, religion, race, and place of birth, abolishing untouchability and making its practice in any form an offense punishable by law. The constitution says, "The state shall strive to promote the welfare of people by securing and protecting as effectively as it may a social order in which justice social, economic and political, shall inform the institutions of the National Life". The quest for social justice, as visualized by Dr. Ambedkar, gives us hope and guarantees it through the constitutional provisions to the hitherto oppressed sections of Indian society such as SC's and ST's and Other Backward Classes. Owing to present situation, it reveals that, social justice ensuring social and economic equality of the depressed classes of people is yet to be fulfilled. Still majority of dalit's living in darkness. Social and economic inequality and discrimination exists even today. Hence, there is a need of re-understanding of Dr. Ambedkar's Concept of social justice.

Key Words: Dr. Ambedkar, Social Justice, Constitution, Egalitarian Society.

About Dr. Ambedkar

Lalit Manisingh, one time the High Commissioner for India in Britain had said, "Dr. Ambedkar was seen to be a man of the stature of Mahatma Gandhi and a great man of India. He has been influenced by history; he studied Thomas Jefferson's 1776 US Bill of Rights and the events of the 1789 French Revolution..... Dr. Ambedkar realized that the Indian Constitution must incorporate the four elements; justice, liberty, equality and fraternity. But above all he knew the absolute necessity of social justice His status was equal to that of Dr. Martin Luther King. Millions of people took upon Ambedkar as a shining light, he was a great democrat, a great patriot and a great man of his people" (N.D.Arora & Awasthy). Vijay Chintaman Snawane writes, "Dr. Ambedkar was truly a multifaceted personality. A great leader and a patriot, a true humanist and none of his contemporaries were parallel to him" (Dr. Jatava).

Ambedkar indeed, a born genius of the time who devoted his whole life for the cause of the upliftment of dalits and weaker sections of the society. His views with regard to social justice stem firm his understanding of the Indian society based on caste system leading to the plight of the dalits.

Concept of Social Justice

Social justice being multi-dimensional concept has been viewed by scholars of law, philosophy and political science. The term social justice refers to the fair and equitable treatment of all individuals in society, ensuring equal rights, opportunities, and resources, regardless of their background or identity. It aims to create a society where everyone can thrive and participate fully in all aspects of life. (Google.com). Social justice is balancing wheel between unequals. It is a great social value in providing a stable society and in securing the unity of the country. In general, social justice may be defined as "the right of the weak, aged, destitute, pro-women, children and other underprivileged persons" (Dr.

Satish Kumar). The tasks of justice are, “the allocation of advantages and disadvantages, reverting the abuse of liberty, the just decision of disputes and adapting change’ (Surendra Singh). Social justice is basically, a term which provides sustenance to justice the rule of law. It has wider connotation in the sense that it includes economic justice also. It aims in removing all kinds of inequalities and affording equal opportunities to all citizens in social as well as in economic affairs. Thus, social justice is stands for equality of all against all kinds of inequalities based on caste, race, sex, power, position, wealth etc. According to John Rawls, the concept of social justice is “all social primary goods—liberty and opportunity, income and wealth, and the basis of self-respect are to be distributed equally unless an unequal distribution of any or all of these goods is to the advantage of the least favored”(John Rawls). Justice Krishna Iyar a former judge of the Supreme Court of India says, “Social justice is not cannot but conscience, not verbal borrowing from like documents but the social force of the supreme law. Social justice is people oriented; legal justice is canalized, controlled and conferred by law” (Krishna Iyar).

Dr. Ambedkar is also one of the exponents of social justice in modern India. According to him, social justice means creating a society based on the principles of liberty, equality and fraternity for all human beings, essentially aiming to eliminate all forms of inequality based on caste, race, sex, power, position and wealth, ensuring equal distribution of social, political and economic resources within a community and for common good([google.com](https://www.google.com)). He was the chief architect of the Indian constitution who was fully aware of the pattern and problems of the Indian society. The aspirations of the different sections of the society and their conflicting interests, he tried to achieve social justice and social democracy in terms of one man one value. He treated social justice as a true basis for patriotism and nationalism. He argued for giving justice to all especially to those who have been denied for centuries; right done for those wrongs, is the spirit of social justice. His concept of social justice advocate a social system which based on right relations between man and man; between class and class and the reorganization of society on the principles of equality, liberty and justice which in turn, necessitates the preferential treatment for the weaker sections of society. Hence, the clauses relating to protective discrimination were made a part of the constitution in whose making Ambedkar presided, especially in the provisions relating to the fundamental rights and directive principles of the state policy.

Constitutional Safeguards for Dalits

A deep study of the constitution as a whole reveals the quest of Dr. Ambedkar for social revolution for the reconstruction of an egalitarian and casteless society through legislative means. The fundamental rights that he whole heartedly supported foster the social reconstruction by gearing the governmental agencies. The Indian constitution empowers the state to make special provisions for generating equality, elimination of discrimination on grounds of religion, race, caste, and sex, place of birth and residence, abolishing untouchability and making its practice in any form an offence punishable by law. The constitution says that, the state shall strive to promote the welfare of people by securing and protecting as effectively as it may a social order in which justice social, economic and political, shall inform the institutions of the national life”(D.C.Ahira).

Dr. Ambedkar had vision for the establishment of social justice through the constitutional provisions in fundamental rights under article 15 prohibition of discrimination on grounds of religion, race, caste, place of birth etc. (2) no citizen shall be subjected to any disability, restriction or condition on grounds only of religion, race, caste, place of birth or any of them. (3) the state is competent under article 15(3), 16(2) and 16(4) to make special provision for women and children. Article 16 provides, equality of opportunity in matters of public employment. It empowers parliament to make a law prescribing

residence within a state a qualification for appointment or any government post. Article 17 abolished untouchability and its practice in any form is forbidden. The enforcement of any disability arising out of untouchability shall be an offence punishable in accordance with law. In exercise of this power, parliament has enacted the untouchability (offences) Act, 1955, which has been amended and renamed (in 1976) as the protection of Civil Rights Act, 1955. Article 46 promotion of educational and economic interests of scheduled castes, scheduled tribes and other weaker sections—the state shall promote with special care the educational and economic interests of the weaker sections of the people, and in particular, of the scheduled castes and the scheduled tribes, and shall protect them from social injustice and all forms of exploitation. Article 330 reserves seats in the House of the people for scheduled castes and scheduled tribes. The number of reserved seats is based on the population of these groups in each state or Union Territory. Article 332, reserves seats for scheduled castes and scheduled tribes in the legislative assemblies of the states. Article 335, applies to appointments to services and posts in connection with the affairs of the Union or of a State. The claims of SCs and STs should be considered when making appointments. The article takes into account equity, justice and merit. It shapes reservation system, including how much to reserve and how to handle unfilled posts. Articles 338, 338a deals with the National Commission for scheduled castes and scheduled tribes. They mandates the establishment and outlines functions, including investigation, safeguards for scheduled castes and scheduled tribes, inquiring into complaints and participating in development planning. These commissions also present annual reports to the president and make recommendations for the protection and welfare of scheduled castes and scheduled tribes (constitutionofindia.etal.in).

Constitutional Safeguards for Women

Dr. Ambedkar, being a philanthropic kind and generous social reformer was much moved with the pitiable and pathetic condition and low status of women in society and he was a torch bearer in the direction of social uplift of women general and Hindu women in particular. Ambedkar chooses his social reform approach only after understanding the reality of the status of women. He was of the opinion that the Hindu women are tied up with bondage of superstitions which they can till their death. They are also responsible for including these wrong notions learned by them through baseless traditions and preaching of the Shashtra's in the budding mind of their offspring. Otherwise, also women in India have remained a matter of joy and a source of amusement at such she was used and misused by men quest to serve their evil ends. She has been used just like machine for procreation. It has also been mentioned in Hindu Shashtra's in that women is the bond slave of her father when she is young to her husband when she is mother(old). Dr. Ambedkar paved the way for Indian women to legally vote, divorce, and own property. He was induced a feminist. In his words, "I measure the progress of a community by the degree of progress which women have achieved"(google.com). Dr. Ambedkar made this statement in a gathering of over 3,000 women in 1927. In another speech in 1936, to communities of Joginis and Devadasis- who typically belonged to the Dalit community – Ambedkar urged these women to fight the regressive religious practice of offering pubescent girls to gods in temples and become "sexually available for community members."He said, "you will ask me how to make your living. I am not going to tell you that. There are hundreds of ways of doing it. But, I, insist that you give up this degraded life.... and do not live under conditions which inevitably drag you into prostitution" (Google.com). Dr. Ambedkar fought tirelessly for the inclusion of rights for women in all different spheres of life. Through his speeches, thoughts and reforms, Ambedkar awakened in women the zeal to fight for social justice and their rights. His reformative measures came in the form of the Hindu Code Bill, meant to modernize the Hindu Society which becomes unparalleled in its importance.

Hence, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's concept of social justice was to emancipate women along with scheduled caste and scheduled tribes is still distant dream.

Dr. Ambedkar, introduced several provisions to safeguard women's rights and promote gender equality. These include the right to equality, prohibition of discrimination, equal opportunity and special provisions in favour of women. Article 14, in general guarantees equal treatment before the law and equal protection of the laws. Article 15 prohibits discrimination on grounds of sex, religion, race, caste, etc. and allows the state to make special provisions for women. Article 16 ensures equal opportunities in matters of public employment for all citizens including women. Right to livelihood and equal pay, under article 39(a) and (b) of the directive principles of state policy, directs the state to ensure an adequate means of livelihood for all citizens and to provide equal pay for equal work for men and women. Free legal aid, article 39A provides for free legal aid to ensure access to justice. Just and human conditions of work and maternity relief, article 42 directs the state to make provisions for ensuring just and human conditions of work and maternity relief.

Renunciation of practices derogatory to women's dignity, article 51(A) (e) a fundamental duty to renounce practices that degrade women's dignity.

Reservation in local bodies (73rd and 74th amendment acts – these amendments provide the reservation of one-third of seats in local bodies for women.

Protection of women from domestic violence act, 2005, provides legal protection for women against domestic violence.

Medical termination of pregnancy act, 1971, allows for safe and legal abortion in certain circumstances. The prohibition of child marriage act, 2006, makes child marriage illegal.

These constitutional provisions, along with various other laws and policies, aim to ensure the rights, dignity and empowerment of women in India.

Social Justice in the Era of Globalization

India is plural society; multi-ethnic, multi-religious and multi-linguistic for which democracy is must for balanced social and regional development. However, democracy cannot survive without social justice. Unfortunately, new economic policy or globalization is bereft of human face, where man is treated as commodity and a person has to compete for the bread on the "Darwinian economic order" i. e. struggle for existence and survival of fittest. Whereas democracy thrives on the co-operative spirit so that strong and weak could survive and co-exist together like tall trees small bushes and grasses growing in the same socio-ecological plain.

The Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes are provided constitutional provisions and safeguards in terms of reservation in services and employment. But what are the outcomes of these reservations, whether, by these reservations, people belonging to these castes are got benefited is the testament of the social justice. The present government statistical data reveals that after 75 years of the commencement of the constitution, the living condition of the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes not yet improved. The data reveals that the proportion of unfilled posts increases as we move up the chain towards more senior posts. According to a 2023 report of the parliamentary committee on welfare of Scheduled castes (SCs) and Scheduled Tribes (STs), the only category of jobs in ministries and departments of the central government where SCs and STs have a share larger than their quota of 15% and 7.5% respectively are the group C jobs excluding safai karmacharies and an even larger share among safai karmacharies are sanitation workers.

Table -1 Share of SC/ST in Central Government Jobs

Category	SC	ST
Group A	13%	5.5%
Group B	17.0	6.9
Group C*	18.6	7.7
Group C**	36.9	6.9
Total	18.4	7.4

*Excluding Safai Karmachari ** Safai Karmachari

Table 1 indicate that, in Group A posts within the central government, scheduled castes constitute approximately 13%, scheduled tribes make up about 5.5% of group A posts, Group B posts SCs constitute 17% and STs 6.9%, Group C* posts (excluding Safai Karmacharies) SCs representation is 18.6% and STs 7.7%, Group C** posts (Safai Karmacharies) SCs represented 36.9% and STs 6.9%. Due to the higher representation of SCs and STs in lower –tier jobs, these groups appear to fill more than their overall quota – 18.4% SCs and 7.4% STs in posts and services under the Central Government. Whereas the reservation policy mandates 15% representation for SCs and 7.5% for STs in all category of positions in central government jobs.

Table – 2 Share of SC/ST in Central University Jobs

Faculty	SC	ST
Teaching Staff	10.9	4.9
Professor	7.4	1.8
Associate Professor	8.0	2.6
Asst. Professor	12.1	5.9
Non Teaching Staff	9.5	9.4
Group A	5.8	4.1
Group B	10.3	5.1
Group C	9.5	5.6

Source: UGC annual report, 2023, Data from 46 Central Universities.

Table 2 indicates the date of the representation of SCs and STs in Teaching and Non- Teaching posts in Central Universities – Data available on 45 Central Universities also shows a similar pattern. SCs constituted 11% of posts and STs less than 5%. The position of professor- SCs constitute 7.4% and STs 1.8%, Associate Professor- SCs 8.0 and STs 2.6%, Assistant Professor- SCs -12.1% and STs 5.9%. The representation in Non- Teaching posts SCs constitute 9.5% and STs 9.4% (Group A SCs -5.8% and STs- 4.1%, Group B SCs – 10.3% and STs – 5.1%, Group C SCs – 9.5% and STs – 5.6%). Once again, the shares are lowest in the senior most positions.

According to the parliamentary report, in spite of special drives relaxation in qualifying criteria and pre-promotional training, ministries or departments were unable to fill the thousand of backlog reserved vacancies.

There are thousands of unfilled posts in govt. because the quotas are not being filled. Clearly, despite having a small section of relatively better off SCs, the government is unable to fill the quota. It is estimated that barely 1.9% of SC earn above Rs. 50,000, most of these would be in government services as historically SCs have no assets, neither land nor business', Pointed out M. S. Nethrapal, and Indian Revenue Services officer who researches issues of Bahujan representation in jobs and education. He added that there was not enough data on the various sub-categories within SC, as data is only collected at a broad level for all SCs as a single category.

The lack of sub-classification leading to the more deprived among SCs or STs missing out would hold true only if the quota was being filled. If the quota was not being filled then nobody could be said to be missing out because someone else was getting through the quota. However, unlike in jobs /posts, the quotas usually get filled when it comes to seats in educational institutions run by govt. like medical colleges, engineering colleges and Universities.

Where quotas are being filled, many Dalit activists support sub-categorization so that castes within the SC category that face greater marginalization could take advantage of the quota and find representation. “Such. Sub-categorization, however, has to be based on the extent of discrimination or marginalization faced by a caste within the SC category. It cannot be based on economic criteria as in the case of OBCs said Nethrapal” (Rama Nagarajan- 2024).

In private sector, there is no such concession. Therefore, government must take policy decision to provide representation to scheduled caste and scheduled tribes in ‘private sector’ too and it may provide social security to them to protect their livelihood.

Status of Social Justice in the wake of Policy revision

Government initiatives and policies are revealing that the Indian government has implemented various affirmative action measures and constitutional provisions to address the historical injustices and promote the welfare of SCs and STs. These include reservations in government jobs and educational institutions, as well as specific schemes and programs aimed at improving their living standards. The National Commission for Scheduled Castes (NCSC) and the National Commission for Scheduled Tribes (NCST) play a crucial role in monitoring the implementation of policies and addressing the concerns of these communities. The ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment is the nodal ministry for overseeing the welfare of Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes.

While there’s improvement, Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes in India, often facing historical marginalization, still experience disparities in living standards, particularly in access to basic amenities, education, and economic condition and healthcare compared to other communities.

A significant portion of SC and ST populations live below the poverty line, especially in rural areas and urban slums. They often lack access to basic necessities like safe drinking water, electricity and sanitation. Indebtedness and bonded labor is also prevalent issues. Literacy rates and educational attainment are lower among SCs and STs compared to the general population. Drop-out rates, particularly among girls remain high. Access to quality education and higher education opportunities can be limited. Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes experience poorer health outcomes, including and maternal mortality. Access to healthcare and sanitation is often limited. Scheduled Castes and Scheduled tribes continue to face discrimination and social exclusion based on caste and tribal identity. Untouchability and other forms of discrimination persist in some areas even today. These deprived communities face challenges in accessing employment and economic opportunities. They are often excluded from the formal economy and forced into low paying jobs. Majority of SCs and STs are working in agriculture as a landless laborers and construction workers in unorganized sectors. People of Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes are often underrepresented in political institutions and decision-making processes. Their voices and concerns are often marginalized.

Conclusion

The basic concept of social justice is to establish egalitarian society. The main objectives’ before Dr. B.R.Ambedkar’s concept of social justice was to uplift scheduled caste, scheduled tribes and women in the society and bring them into the mainstream society. For that Dr.B.R.Ambedkar sacrificed his whole

life for the cause of social justice. His struggle for social justice could be visualized in the ideas and philosophy of the Indian constitution.

In practice, the task of Dr. B.R.Ambedkar's concept of social justice for the SC's and ST's and women not yet really fulfilled, the reason may be many, one of the reason is lack of political will and vested interest of political parties and their successive governments. It is the failure on the part of governments for not establishing social justice even after several decades of India's' freedom. The lack of awareness among the deprived sections 'rights is one more reason for un-accomplishment of social justice. The era of globalization further side lined the concept of social justice, because, existing public sector industries that generated employment opportunities for masses is being privatized. The process of privatization benefited the private owners and multi-national companies as their one and only objective is to gain profit and service is not yet all their priority. The private sectors in turn, insist for merits which discard the concept of social justice. Unfortunately new economic policy in backdrop of globalization is bereft of human face, where man is treated as commodity and a person has to compete for the bread, on the "Darwinian socio-economic order" i.e. struggle for existence and survival of the fittest. Where, the weaker section of the society continues to be suffered and struggle for exist. The time has come to the scheduled caste and scheduled tribes to fight for survival with the invincible weapon of Dr. B.R.Ambedka's thoughts. Through, his ideals unaccomplished task of social justice is to be accomplished.

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DR.B.R. AMBEDKAR VISION FOR INDIAN DEMOCRACY: IDEALS OF FEDERALISM AND SOCIAL JUSTICE**Vimochan Ashok Asode**

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Abstract

As a trailblazing drafter of the Indian Constitution, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar envisioned a democratic system based on social justice and federalism. His intellectual contributions are examined in this essay with a focus on their applicability to modern government and social justice. The study emphasizes his dedication to eliminating social hierarchies and guaranteeing fair resource distribution within a federal structure by examining his writings, speeches, and constitutional contributions. Mostly, the people are being treated with discrimination in size, color, caste, religion, race in the society because of they are mostly uneducated and from marginalized sections of the society that creates a social disorder and inequality among them. Hence, the need of the social justice is an inevitable and is the only weapon to prosper the people towards their active participation in the development and mainstream of the society. However, it becomes important to establish an egalitarian social, economic and political order in diverse society like India. It's in this backdrop the article tries to explore the concept of social justice and federal system Ambedkar view on it. How far Ambedkar's reflection is visible in Indian federalism system and its relevance in the present times.

Keywords: *Dr.B.R.Ambedkar, Indian democracy, federalism, social justice, Constitution of India and social equality.*

Introduction

Social justice is an application of distributive justice to wealth, assets, privileges and advantages within a society or a state. The essence of justice is the attainment of common good for all. Social justice involves the creation of a just and fair social order and provides justice for every member of the community. Social justice involves removing inequalities in society and affording equal opportunities to all individuals in social, economic and political affairs of society.

Indian society is divided into castes and communities, which create walls and barriers of exclusiveness within society on the basis of superiority and inferiority. Social justice in India is the product of social injustice of the caste system. Such social inequalities pose a serious threat not only to society but also to Indian democracy. Under the traditional Hindu caste hierarchy, backward communities and women have suffered for centuries because they were denied equality, education and other opportunities for advancement. Social justice in the context of Indian society provides benefits, facilities, concessions, privileges and special rights to those who were denied these for centuries. If opportunities are not given to develop their neglected talents there will remain social imbalance in Indian society

As India struggles with issues like regionalism, socioeconomic inequality, and social inequalities, Ambedkar's vision is still relevant today. His principles of social justice, federalism, and democracy are still essential to preserving and strengthening India's democratic foundation. In order to provide insights into how Ambedkar's principles might guide future changes, this study aims to examine his vision, evaluate its execution, and investigate its applicability in tackling today's issues.

This work provides an extensive understanding of Ambedkar's contributions and their sustainable impact upon Indian governance and society through an extensive review of primary and secondary sources.

Objectives of the study

1. Examine Ambedkar's perspective of democracy as a means of gaining dignity, equality, and fraternity in a very hierarchical society.
2. Examine his leadership in integrating federalism and social justice into the Constitution
3. To study Ambedkar's contributions to the federal structure of India, balancing unity with regional autonomy.
4. To analyze Dr. Ambedkar's conceptualization of federalism within the Indian context.
5. To explore his advocacy for social justice and its incorporation into the Indian Constitution.
6. Examine how Ambedkar viewed federalism as a way to overcome social injustices and regional inequities in order to promote social justice.
7. To evaluate the contemporary relevance of his vision in addressing socio-political inequalities.

Research Methodology

I have combined two of the most well-known social science research methodologies for this investigation since they are a reliable and efficient approach to gathering data from several individuals in a convenient and logical manner.

The research framework study is based on the primary and secondary sources that are currently accessible. Dr. Ambedkar's speeches, writings, and contributions to the Constituent Assembly debates, public records, government acts, and directives were the main sources that were made available. To supplement the findings, interviews with the respondents were conducted. The survey was carried out in addition to participant observation and informal group discussions. Conversely, print items such as books, academic papers, biographies, and books on Indian democracy and Ambedkar's philosophy, unpublished theses, journals, periodicals, and the internet were used as secondary sources of information.

Dr. Ambedkar's Perspective on Democracy:

Dr. Ambedkar made the following statement in reference to democracy: "I believe that the existence of tyranny of the majority over the minority is a fundamental requirement for democracy to function." The minority must always feel secure in understanding that, despite the majority maintaining power, neither morals nor the minority will be compromised. "Democracy is not a form of government, but a form of social organization," he added. Dr. Ambedkar always adopted a socialistic stance, which is seen in his remarks regarding democracy. According to him, democracy is necessary to enact social justice.

According to Dr. Ambedkar, social and economic democracy are necessary for political democracy to be successful. According to him, the most effective way to accomplish socio-economic democracy is to attain political democracy in the initial phase. Without political, social, and economic democracy, residents of any country cannot enjoy their rights, which is why these concepts are so important. To fulfill the principles of equality and fraternity established in the Preamble of our Constitution, all three democracies must coexist.

Concept of Federalism in India:

Federalism is a type of government that distributes power between a central authority and regional political units. Indian Federalism differs from that of other countries, such as the US.

The Indian form of federalism is known as a quasi-federal system, as it has elements of both a federation and a union.

Article 1 of the Constitution of India states that 'India that is Bharat shall be a union of states'. Indian federation was not a product of coming together of states to form the federal union of India. It was rather a conversion of a unitary system into a federal system.

It is a compromise between two conflicting considerations such as autonomy enjoyed by states within the constitutionally prescribed limit (State List) and the need for a strong centre in view of the unity and integrity of the country.

Federalism is the most important aspect of modern constitutionalism. The primary goals of Indian federalism are unity in diversity, devolution of authority, and decentralization of administration. Through federalism, the State pursues the objective of shared welfare in the midst of significant variety in sociocultural and economic domains.

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar's Views on Federalism

In his speech on November 4, 1948, Dr. Ambedkar discussed in detail the key elements of the proposed federation. He said that insofar as it aimed to create a dual polity with the Union at the center and the State at its periphery, each with the sovereign authority to execute its powers in its own domain, the Draft Constitution represented an unquestionably federal constitution. It stood out from other federations as a result of a few unique characteristics. As a result, the Draft Constitution authorized the anticipated Indian Federation to become a unitary state in the event of a serious emergency or war. Once more, the proposed Constitution offered several tools to get beyond the inherent rigidity of federalism, some of which were borrowed from the Australian Constitution and others of which were entirely original.

These included, among other things, offering Parliament the sole authority to enact laws on a broad range of topics; putting fundamental laws—both civil and criminal—under existing jurisdiction to guarantee consistency in all fundamental matters; providing for a comparatively simple amendment process; and granting Parliament the authority to enact laws on topics even during regular times. A single judiciary, certain common All India Civil Services, and a single Indian citizenship were other unique characteristics.

Ambedkar claimed that the Draft Constitution had fairly balanced the claims of the Center and the units, refuting the charge that the Center had been made too strong. Even if the Center was not granted greater authority and responsibilities than were officially required, the modern world made centralized power unavoidable, and the trend would undoubtedly continue in India regardless of the Constitution's restrictions. Articles 352 to 360 of Part XVIII of the Constitution address emergency situations, including financial emergencies, national emergencies, and emergencies for states in the event that the constitutional machinery fails.

These provisions, which allowed the President to rule over the state (under Article 356 when circumstances arise that the state cannot be carried on in accordance with the Constitution), greatly alarmed the founders of the Constitution, who feared that they would undermine the federal character of our document. It was their hope that this would never be implemented.

The historic speech that Dr. Ambedkar gave at a time when many members of the Constituent Assembly rejected this article is quoted below. "I share the sentiments that such articles will never be called into operation and that they remain a dead letter," Dr. Ambedkar had stated at the time. I trust that the President, who has these powers, will exercise caution before suspending the Province's administration, if they are ever put into effect. I hope that his first action will be to simply tell a province

that has made a mistake that things are not proceeding as the Constitution intended. His second option, should that warning prove ineffective, would be to call an election so that the province's citizens may resolve their differences on their own. He should only use this article if the other two cures are ineffective.

Dr. B. R. Ambedkar' thoughts on Social Justice

It is generally assumed that B.R. Ambedkar neither defined social justice the way Rawls or Miller did nor applied it in Indian context. However, his political philosophy and social doctrine invoke justice in myriad contexts – sometimes in direct and specific illustration of justice and equality and often in his worldview and political action. The same is reflected in the preamble to the Indian constitution, where justice is invoked in terms of social, economic and political which is comprehensive and unambiguous. Ambedkar invokes the principle of social justice in various contexts. He primarily used it in the context of

- Abolition of Untouchability and Caste System
- legal education,
- land ownership,
- Political agency for depressed classes and religion.

Abolition of Untouchability and Caste System

A key component of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar's vision of social justice and equality was his support for the repeal of the caste system and untouchability. He believed that these traditions, which denied Dalits (Scheduled Castes) access to resources, education, and public areas, were the main drivers of oppression and injustice in Indian society.

Ambedkar advocated social reform initiatives, such as the Mahad Satyagraha for water rights and temple admission campaigns, to address these inequalities, highlighting political representation and education as means of empowering people. In his capacity as the head of the Indian Constitution's drafting committee, he made sure that Article 17 was included, which specifically outlawed untouchability and made its practice illegal. In order to give underprivileged groups chances, he also promoted affirmative action through reservations. Ambedkar thought that although legal changes were necessary, a fundamental shift in the way society viewed caste and equality was necessary for true social justice.

Legal Education

In reference to legal profession and legal education, Ambedkar emphasises on the need for social justice in legal education and need for inclusion and self representation of marginalized groups in legal profession. He opines:

The problem of overcrowding of the Legal Profession must be separated from the problems of legal education. It would be indefensible both from the stand-point of education and also from the stand-point of social justice to frame a scheme of Legal Education on a basis which would make legal profession the preserve of the few (Ambedkar, 2014, Vol.17 (2):7).

Land ownership

In constituent assembly debates, in a discussion on article 31 B of draft constitution, pertaining to the question of abolishment of estates and removal of intermediaries in zamindari system, Ambedkar observes: Property in land particularly is not a Fundamental Right. Article 43 of the Irish Constitution clause (2), states that the exercise of the right mentioned, that is the right on land, should be regulated by the principles of social justice (Ambedkar, 2014, vol.15:354).

Political agency for depressed classes

Emphasising on the need for political awareness among the ex-untouchables to remove social injustice in Indian society, Ambedkar writes: Two agencies are generally relied upon by the social idealists for producing social justice. One is reason, the other is religion (Ambedkar, 2014, Vol. 5:397).

In his understanding, these two agencies are insufficient and ineffective to produce social justice in Indian society. He explains, The rationalists who uphold the mission of reason believe that injustice could be eliminated by the increasing power of intelligence. In the mediaeval age social injustice and superstition were intimately related to each other. It was natural for the rationalists to believe that the elimination of superstition must result in the abolition of injustice. This belief was encouraged by the results. Today it has become the creed of the educationists, philosophers, psychologists and social scientists who believe that universal education and the development of printing and press would result in an ideal society, in which every individual would be so enlightened that there would be no place for social injustice (Ambedkar, 2014, Vol. 5:397).

In order to establish an ideal or just society, he also discusses social justice. A just society, in his opinion, is one that is devoid of caste and founded on the ideas of social justice as well as a fusion of the three elements of liberty, equality, and fraternity. His ideal society, however, is founded on two fundamental ideas: first, that each person is an end in himself, and second, that society's goal and object is each person's personal development.

The second is that considerations based on liberty, equality, and fraternity must be taken into account while evaluating the terms of associated existence among members of society. Ambedkar once more held that access to knowledge, economic equality, and social equality are the three fundamental requirements that make individual liberty a reality. According to Ambedkar, the only thing that keeps anarchy at bay and supports moral order among men is brotherhood. Individualism leads to chaos. An ideal society is unthinkable without fraternity, which is a crucial aspect of social justice. Accordingly, social justice for him entails a radical shift in our perspective and attitude toward people and things as well as a fundamental shift in the ideas that underpin individual life.

Ambedkar's concept of social justice included-

1. Unity and equality of all human beings.
2. Equal worth of men and women.
3. Respect for the weak and the lowly.
4. Regards for human rights.
5. Benevolence, mutual love, sympathy, tolerance and charity towards fellow beings.
6. Human treatment in all cases.
7. Dignity of all citizens.
8. Abolition of caste distinction.
9. Education and property for all.
10. Good will and gentleness.

Findings:

- Ambedkar defined democracy as going beyond electoral politics and encompassing socioeconomic equality. He envisioned a society built on liberty, equality, and fraternity as the fundamental basis of governance.
- Ambedkar proposed a federal structure that balanced state sovereignty and central power, allowing India's cultural and linguistic variety while encouraging national cohesion.

- Ambedkar's crusade for social justice concentrated on resolving systemic disparities, particularly caste discrimination, through constitutional safeguards such as reservations and equal rights.
- While affirmative action and decentralization have helped to implement Ambedkar's objectives, obstacles remain in areas such as regional imbalances, caste-based violence, and inadequate implementation of social justice legislation.
- Ambedkar's principles continue to be useful in dealing with regionalism, caste inequality, and economic imbalances, highlighting their timeless applicability. Ambedkar's ideas have been foundational in structuring India's democratic framework, influencing provisions for fundamental rights and the Directive Principles of State Policy.
- Ambedkar's thoughts on democracy and justice resonate with global discourses on human rights and federal governance.

Recommendations:

- ❖ Strengthen affirmative action policies (e.g., reservations for Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, and Other Backward Classes) to ensure equitable representation in education, employment, and political systems.
- ❖ Strict enforcement of laws against caste-based discrimination, untouchability, and gender-based violence.
- ❖ Universal access to quality education, healthcare, and sanitation, especially in marginalized communities.
- ❖ Strengthen the implementation of the Right to Education Act and public health initiatives targeting vulnerable groups.
- ❖ Emphasized the importance of social justice and equitable federalism, recommending greater decentralization and improved affirmative action policies.

Conclusion

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar's vision for Indian democracy remains a cornerstone of India's constitutional and democratic ethos. His ideals of federalism and social justice are not only integral to India's progress but also serve as a guiding light for nations grappling with diversity and inequality. Strengthening these principles in contemporary times is imperative for realizing his dream of an inclusive and equitable society.

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RELIGIOUS IDENTITY AND ELECTORAL POLITICS IN KARNATAKA**Dr. Jagdeesha H**

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Abstract

Religious identity has increasingly become a critical factor in the electoral politics of Karnataka, a state marked by its demographic diversity and intricate social dynamics. With Hindus forming the majority, alongside substantial Muslim, Christian, and Jain populations, religious affiliation often intersects with caste and regional identities to shape political behavior and party strategies. Major political parties, such as the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), Indian National Congress (INC), and Janata Dal (Secular) [JD(S)], have capitalized on these religious and caste affiliations to secure voter bases.

The BJP's rise in Karnataka is tied to its emphasis on Hindutva, which has fostered religious polarization, particularly in regions like coastal Karnataka. Meanwhile, the Congress has positioned itself as a secular party, drawing support from religious minorities, while JD(S) has relied on its regional base, appealing to both caste and religious groups. This article explores the role of religious identity in Karnataka's electoral politics, analyzing how political parties have mobilized religious communities and the implications for the state's political landscape. The study highlights how religious identity, combined with caste and regional factors, continues to be a decisive element in shaping electoral outcomes in Karnataka.

Key words: Religious identity, electoral politics, Karnataka, Hindutva, secular.

Introduction

Religious identity plays a pivotal role in shaping the electoral politics of Karnataka, a state characterized by its diverse population and complex social fabric. With a majority Hindu population alongside significant Muslim, Christian, and Jain communities, religion often intertwines with caste and regional identities, influencing political alignments and voting behaviors. Over the years, political parties like the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), Indian National Congress (INC), and Janata Dal (Secular) [JD(S)] have strategically engaged with religious identities to build vote banks, often aligning these efforts with caste-based politics.

The rise of Hindu nationalism, spearheaded by the BJP, has particularly transformed the political landscape, with religious polarization becoming a key electoral tool in certain regions. At the same time, Congress has traditionally positioned itself as a secular force, seeking support from religious minorities such as Muslims and Christians. The regional JD(S) has also played a role by appealing to both caste and religious identities, particularly in the Old Mysore region.

In this context, understanding how religious identity influences political strategies and electoral outcomes in Karnataka provides valuable insights into the broader dynamics of Indian democracy. This article delves into the historical and contemporary intersections of religion and politics in Karnataka, examining how religious communities have shaped the state's electoral trends over time.

Religious Composition of Karnataka

Understanding the religious demography of Karnataka is crucial to understanding its electoral politics. As per the 2011 Census, Karnataka's population is largely Hindu, with significant Muslim and Christian minorities, and smaller Jain and other religious groups.

Religion	Percentage of Population
Hindus	84%
Muslims	13%
Christians	1.9%

Jains	0.72%
Others	0.38%

The state's political landscape reflects this diversity, as various parties attempt to consolidate votes across these religious communities, often aligning with caste dynamics to form cohesive electoral strategies.

The Role of Religion in Karnataka's Political Landscape

Karnataka's political landscape is dominated by three key parties: the **Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP)**, the **Indian National Congress (INC)**, and the **Janata Dal (Secular) [JD(S)]**. Each of these parties has leveraged religious identity differently, influencing electoral outcomes in varying ways.

1. The Rise of BJP: Hindu Nationalism and Religious Consolidation

The **Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP)** has positioned itself as the principal party for consolidating the Hindu vote. The rise of the BJP in Karnataka is deeply linked to the broader national trend of Hindu nationalism. The party's electoral success in the state, especially after the 1990s, can be attributed to its ability to mobilize the Hindu majority by tapping into communal sentiments and emphasizing the cultural unity of Hindus.

A key element of the BJP's strategy has been its alignment with the **Lingayat** community, a dominant caste group within the Hindu fold. Lingayats have historically played a crucial role in the state's politics and have been a major base for the BJP, particularly in northern Karnataka. In addition to Lingayats, the BJP has made concerted efforts to reach out to **Vokkaligas**, another powerful Hindu caste group, though this community has traditionally aligned with JD(S).

The **Ayodhya movement** in the 1990s, which centered on the construction of a Ram temple on the disputed Babri Masjid site, had a significant impact on Karnataka's electoral politics. It catalyzed the rise of Hindu nationalism in the state, particularly in coastal Karnataka, where communal tensions between Hindus and Muslims have flared periodically. The **communal riots** in coastal Karnataka in the late 1990s and early 2000s further polarized the electorate, helping the BJP consolidate the Hindu vote.

Additionally, incidents such as the **Mangalore church attacks in 2008**, which involved vandalism of Christian institutions, highlighted religious tensions and reinforced the BJP's Hindutva agenda. In coastal Karnataka, the BJP's success is partially built on its ability to project itself as the defender of Hindu values, positioning Muslims and Christians as external threats to Hindu culture.

2. Congress: Champion of Secularism and Minority Rights

The **Indian National Congress (INC)**, on the other hand, has traditionally followed a secular approach, advocating for the protection and inclusion of religious minorities such as Muslims and Christians. The Congress has historically received strong support from these communities, particularly in regions like Hyderabad-Karnataka, where Muslims form a significant part of the electorate.

Under the leadership of **Siddaramaiah**, who served as Chief Minister from 2013 to 2018, the Congress government in Karnataka pursued an **Ahinda** strategy, aimed at consolidating the support of **minorities, backward classes, and Dalits**. The term Ahinda stands for "**Alpasankhyataru**" (minorities), **Hindulidavaru** (backward classes), and **Dalitaru** (Dalits). This strategy sought to challenge the dominance of the BJP and JD(S) by focusing on marginalized groups, many of whom identify as religious minorities.

Congress's social welfare programs, such as **Anna Bhagya** (free rice distribution) and **Ksheera Bhagya** (free milk distribution), were aimed at economically disadvantaged groups, including religious minorities, to build a broad-based coalition that could counter the BJP's Hindu consolidation.

Congress's secularism and inclusive approach have historically helped it win support from Muslims and Christians, especially in urban centers like Bengaluru and in regions with significant minority populations.

However, Congress's efforts to consolidate minority votes have occasionally led to charges of **appeasement politics**, especially from the BJP. The latter has often accused Congress of engaging in vote-bank politics by focusing too much on minority rights, thereby alienating the majority Hindu electorate.

3. JD(S): A Regional Player and the Caste-Religious Nexus

The **Janata Dal (Secular) [JD(S)]**, led by former Prime Minister **H.D. Deve Gowda** and his son **H.D. Kumaraswamy**, has traditionally been a regional player with a stronghold in the **Old Mysore region**, particularly among the **Vokkaliga** community. While JD(S) is primarily a caste-based party, it has also sought to appeal to religious minorities, particularly Muslims, in regions where they form a significant portion of the electorate.

The JD(S) has been particularly successful in forming coalitions between Vokkaligas and Muslims, as both groups have historically had little overlap with the BJP's Hindu nationalist base. This coalition-building strategy has allowed JD(S) to maintain a foothold in parts of southern Karnataka, particularly in areas like **Mandya, Hassan, and Ramanagara**. However, the party's influence remains largely regional, and it has struggled to make significant inroads beyond its Vokkaliga-Muslim base.

The Caste and Religious Intersection: The Lingayat Debate

Religious identity in Karnataka is not purely about religious beliefs; it also intersects with caste identity. This is most evident in the **Lingayat** community's push for recognition as a separate religion. The **Lingayats**, who follow the teachings of 12th-century social reformer **Basava**, consider themselves distinct from mainstream Hinduism due to their rejection of the caste system and Brahmanical rituals.

In the run-up to the **2018 Karnataka Assembly elections**, the Congress government led by Siddaramaiah endorsed the demand for separate religious status for Lingayats. The move was widely seen as an attempt to split the BJP's traditional Lingayat vote bank by appealing to those Lingayats who favored being recognized as a separate religion. While the demand for separate status did not ultimately shift the electoral outcome significantly, it highlighted the complex relationship between caste and religion in Karnataka politics.

Lingayat Separate Religion Movement Timeline	Key Events
Early 20th Century	Lingayat leaders demand separate religious identity.
2017-2018	Congress government backs the demand for religious status.
Post-2018	BJP opposes the move, saying it divides Hindus.

Regional Variations in Religious Influence

Religious influence on electoral politics in Karnataka varies significantly by region. Coastal Karnataka, for instance, has witnessed intense communal polarization, largely driven by BJP's Hindutva politics. This region has seen several communal clashes between Hindus and Muslims, which have helped the BJP consolidate its Hindu base.

The **Old Mysore region**, by contrast, is dominated by caste politics, particularly the influence of Vokkaligas, and religious identity plays a less prominent role. Here, JD(S) has traditionally been strong, with both Vokkaligas and Muslims forming the party's key vote banks.

The **Hyderabad-Karnataka region** (now referred to as **Kalyana-Karnataka**) is another critical battleground. This region has a significant Muslim population, and the Congress has traditionally done well here by positioning itself as a secular alternative to the BJP.

Region	Religious Influence on Politics
Coastal Karnataka	High religious polarization, BJP's stronghold.
Old Mysore	Caste-dominated, with JD(S) appealing to Vokkaligas and Muslims.
Hyderabad-Karnataka	Congress stronghold, with significant Muslim population.

Conclusion

Religious identity continues to be a defining factor in Karnataka's electoral politics. From the BJP's Hindu nationalist appeal to Congress's secularism and JD(S)'s regional caste-religious coalitions, religious communities have a profound influence on party strategies and voter behavior. The interplay between religion and caste adds complexity to the state's political landscape, making it a microcosm of the broader patterns seen in Indian electoral politics.

As Karnataka moves toward future elections, the influence of religious identity will likely remain a central feature, shaping alliances, voter preferences, and the overall political discourse. The ability of political parties to navigate these religious dynamics, while balancing caste and regional identities, will continue to be critical in determining their success.

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THE ROLE OF PANCHAYAT DEVELOPMENT OFFICERS IN RURAL DEVELOPMENT: A CASE STUDY OF MYSORE

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Abstract

Panchayat Raj Institutions (PRIs) are an integral part of democratic local governance system. It has been a cornerstone of rural development. PRIs were introduced by the 73rd Constitutional Amendment, 1992 to establish a three-tier system of local self-governance in India. Karnataka Panchayat Raj Act, 1993 has facilitated people's participation at grass-root levels. The Karnataka government introduced Panchayat Development Officers (PDOs) in 2008 instrumental at executing Gram Swaraj initiatives. PDOs appointed to each Gram Panchayat play a key role in guiding elected representatives, implementing development related schemes and bridging the gap between the government and the people. By empowering Panchayats and supporting elected representatives, PDOs contribute significantly to rural development. Panchayat Development Officers play a very important role in the development of rural areas in Karnataka. As they are the executive officers of the Gram Panchayats, their contribution to the overall development of rural areas is indispensable.

Key words: Panchayat, Rural Government, Programme, Development, Technology.

Introduction

Improving the quality of life of rural people is the most important agenda of rural development programme. Rural development implies economic emancipation and social transformation. Rural development is a dynamic process and PDOs fasten the process by engaging with stakeholders- rural households, government, women groups, communities. Panchayat Development Officers are the backbone of rural development in India. These government officials are appointed to Gram Panchayats to oversee and implement various development programs. They play an important role in implementing government policies and programs at the grassroots level. Government programs focussing infrastructure development, education, healthcare, agriculture, and rural non-farm activities are implemented by the PDOs.

Literature Review

Sivanna (2008) "The Government of Karnataka has made sincere efforts to move towards the attainment of the spirit of Article 243 G of the 73rd Amendment for making its panchayat as real centres of institutions of self-government engaged in promoting economic development in the rural areas and also to ensure social justice in distributing the benefits of development to all the sections of society, including the vulnerable ones." The article provides insights into the various aspects of decision-making, policy formulation and policy implementation with respect to rural development initiatives and the comprehensive understanding of the role of institutions.

Panda, Santanu and Majumder (2013) "The Rural development generally refers to the process of improving the quality of life and economic well-being of people living in relatively isolated and sparsely populated areas." The role of PDOs is crucial given the nature of their functioning in assimilating and penetration of government schemes and policies.

Sarkar (2017) "Panchayat Raj Institutions- the grass-roots units of local self-government have been proclaimed as the vehicles of socio-economic transformation in rural India." The executive body of PDOs is instrumental in ensuring democratic decentralisation.

Krishnamurthy S and Manjappa S (2019) “India is the nations of villages and soul of India lives its villages. In true sense, without progress and prosperity of the villages, the countries prosperity and well-being is inconceivable.” The cooperative federalism in India becomes more meaningful on grass-root participation and democratic decentralisation wherein the role of PDOs is pivotal.

Research Methodology:

This study surveyed 125 PDOs in Mysore district to understand their role of PDOs in rural development.

Primary Sources: The primary data has been collected from the Panchayat Development Officers working in different Panchayats in Mysore district. Hence, the research study is based on survey of PDOs and as the PDOs are highly educated, collection of primary data was made by using questionnaire as research tool.

Secondary Sources: The secondary sources of data considered for the research are books, research papers, journal articles, research reports, web sites, etc.

Table No. 1. Gram Panchayats and Panchayat Development Officers (PDOs) in Mysore and Samples of PDOs Surveyed for the Study

Taluk	No. of PDOs	PDOs Surveyed for the Research Study
H D Kote	25	13
Hunsur	38	20
K R Nagar	15	8
T Narasipura	32	16
Mysore	27	14
Saligrama	19	10
Saraguru	12	6
Nanjangud	41	21
Piriyapatna	34	17

Source:

1. Panchatantra Website, RDPR - Government of Karnataka.
2. Personal Visit to Zilla Panchayat, Mysore.

Key Findings:

- Demographics: Most PDOs are young, educated, married, and live in nuclear families. Many have postgraduate degrees.
- Recruitment and Experience: PDOs are recruited through a merit-based process. Most have 7-15 years of experience.
- Financial Management: PDOs are generally aware of Panchayat finances, budget preparation, and fund allocation. However, some rely on Panchayat members' decisions.
- Role in Development: PDOs actively monitor development projects but some delegate decision-making to Panchayat members.
- Adherence to Rules: Most PDOs follow government rules and guidelines, but some are influenced by Panchayat members.

PDOs are responsible for implementing various rural development schemes of the Central and State Governments at the Gram Panchayat level. They efficiently manage and transparently utilize the grants released for the schemes. They organize Gram Sabhas, listen to the problems of the villagers and find solutions to them. They take steps for the development of infrastructure like drinking water, sewage system, roads, schools, health centres etc. They empower rural people through self-help groups, women empowerment programmes. They preserve and update all the records of the Gram Panchayat. They

collect taxes and other income due to the Gram Panchayat. PDOs reach out to the people about various schemes of the government to inform the people about various schemes of the Central and State Government and encourage them to avail the schemes. In simple terms, PDOs have to do all the work required for the overall development of the Gram Panchayat. They work as the eyes, ears and hands of the Gram Panchayat.

Training

The Abdul Nazir Sab State Rural Development and Panchayat Raj Training Institute, Mysuru, established in 1989, is an autonomous body under the Ministry of Rural Development, Government of India, and the Government of Karnataka. It focuses on providing training for district, taluk, and village panchayat officials, with an emphasis on effective implementation of government schemes and capacity building. The institute organizes basic three-month training for newly appointed PDOs, conducts research, workshops, seminars, and publishes various materials, including books and e-learning content. Key training topics include the structure and functioning of Panchayat Raj Institutions, rural development schemes, the use of technology in panchayat operations, financial management, legal frameworks, leadership skills, and community relations. Specialized training is also provided in areas like solid waste management and rural health training. Workshops, lectures, and online platforms are the primary methods of training, with a focus on interactive learning, practical application, and sharing experiences across different districts. The continuous training improves the skills of PDOs, enhances the transparency and accountability of village panchayats, and strengthens their role in rural development. It fosters better relationships with rural communities, ensuring their active participation. Regular evaluation through performance assessments and questionnaires helps track the effectiveness of the training.

Discussion:

The study highlights the importance of PDOs in rural development. However, it also reveals challenges such as the influence of Panchayat members on decision-making and potential disregard for rules. To enhance the role of PDOs, it is crucial to:

- **Strengthen Training:** Provide comprehensive training to PDOs on financial management, project implementation, and adherence to government rules.
- **Empower PDOs:** Empower PDOs to take independent decisions and reduce the influence of Panchayat members.
- **Accountability Mechanisms:** Implement robust accountability mechanisms to ensure transparency and efficiency in Panchayat operations.
- **Regular Monitoring:** Conduct regular monitoring and evaluation of Panchayat activities to identify and address issues.
- **Public Awareness:** Create awareness among the public about the role of PDOs and their accountability.

Specific Challenges Faced by PDOs:

- **Regional Variations:** It is crucial to delve deeper into the specific challenges faced by PDOs in different regions of India. Regional disparities in terms of infrastructure, socio-economic conditions, and cultural factors can significantly impact the work of PDOs.
- **Capacity Building Needs:** A detailed analysis of the capacity-building needs of PDOs can help identify specific training and skill development programs to address their challenges.

- **Interpersonal Skills:** Effective communication and interpersonal skills are essential for PDOs to interact with various stakeholders, including Panchayat members, government officials, and community members.

Impact of Technology on PDOs' Work:

- **E-Governance Initiatives:** Assessing the potential of e-governance initiatives to enhance transparency, accountability, and efficiency in rural development programs.
- **Digital Tools and Platforms:** Exploring how digital tools and platforms can be used to streamline administrative tasks, improve data management, and facilitate communication between PDOs and other stakeholders
- **Cyber security Concerns:** Addressing the cyber security risks associated with the increasing use of technology in rural areas and developing strategies to protect sensitive information.

Public Participation in Rural Development:

- **Social Mobilization:** Exploring the role of social mobilization in creating awareness about government schemes and encouraging community participation.
- **Empowering Women:** Highlighting the importance of empowering women in rural areas to participate actively in decision-making and development processes.
- **Community Engagement:** Discussing effective strategies to engage with rural communities and involve them in decision-making processes.

Monitoring and Evaluation of Rural Development Programs:

- **Accountability and Transparency:** Implementing effective mechanisms to ensure accountability and transparency in the implementation of rural development programs.
- **Performance Indicators:** Developing robust performance indicators to measure the impact of rural development programs.

Researchers, policymakers, and practitioners can understand the challenges and opportunities faced by PDOs as a result of such studies. This knowledge can inform the development of evidence-based policies and strategies to improve the effectiveness of rural development programs in India. Furthermore, such studies help realise the lacunae in the institution of Panchayat Development Officer and helps rectify structural and functional aspects of the institution; procedural and substantial dimensions of the institution and the future course of action.

Conclusion

Panchayat Development Officers are pivotal in rural development. To optimize their role, the following recommendations can be implemented:

- **Strengthening Gram Sabha:** Regular Gram Sabhas should be conducted to encourage community participation in decision-making and to address local issues.
- **Community Awareness:** Conduct programs to raise awareness about issues like health, hygiene, education, and social equality.
- **Infrastructure Development:** Prioritize development of basic amenities like water, electricity, roads, and healthcare facilities.
- **Agriculture and Livestock Development:** Promote modern agricultural practices, support farmer's cooperatives, and encourage livestock rearing.
- **Women Empowerment:** Effective functioning of self-help groups, further penetration of skill development programs, and promotion of their participation in decision-making can facilitate empowerment of women.

- **Education and Healthcare:** Improve school infrastructure and healthcare facilities, and promote health awareness programs.
- **Effective Implementation of Government Schemes:** Ensure that government schemes reach the intended beneficiaries.
- **Corruption Prevention:** Promote transparency and accountability in panchayat administration.
- **Technology Integration:** Utilize technology for efficient governance and service delivery.
- **Coordination with Cooperatives:** Collaborate with cooperatives to enhance rural development. PDOs can thus disseminate knowledge about policies of the state and central government to the rural masses.
- **Priority-Based Action Plans:** Develop action plans based on the most pressing needs of the community. The PDOs can select beneficiaries/target-groups, manage project funds and monitor periodic progress of programmes in a more systematic manner across space and time.
- **Regular Audits:** Conduct regular audits to ensure financial accountability.
- **Capacity Building:** Provide regular training to PDOs and panchayat members.
- **Public Grievance Redressal:** Establish a system for addressing public grievances promptly.
- **PDO Welfare:** Establish a welfare fund for PDOs and provide incentives for good performance.
- **Adequate Funding:** Ensure adequate funding for rural development programs.

By implementing these recommendations, PDOs can play a more effective role in driving rural development, improving the quality of life of rural communities, and fostering sustainable development. PDOs can contribute to the overall development of rural areas, leading to improved quality of life for rural communities.

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STUDY OF THE TRENDS OF WOMEN EMPOWERMENT IN INDIA**Dr. Shivanna**

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Abstract

The principle of gender equality is enshrined in the Indian Constitution in its Preamble, Fundamental Rights, Fundamental Duties and Directive Principles. The Constitution not only grants equality to women, but also empowers the state to adopt measures of positive discrimination in favor of women. 'Empowerment' may be described as a process which helps people to assert their control over the factors which affect their lives. Empowerment of women means developing them as more aware individuals, who are politically active, economically productive and independent and are able to make intelligent discussion in matters that affect them. Present article discusses about various initiatives taken by Government of India for empowering women by analyzing position of India in Gender Inequality Index and Global Gender Gap Index of United Nations. Article concludes with the note that due recognition must be given to women and society should come forward to ensure equal status for women in all spheres of life.

Key Words: National Movement, Dignity of Women, National Commission for Women, Human Development, Gender Parity, Dowry Harassment.

Introduction

Women constitute almost 50% of the world's population but India has shown disproportionate sex ratio whereby female's population has been comparatively lower than males. As far as their social status is concerned, they are not treated as equal to men in all the places. In the Western societies, the women have got equal right and status with men in all walks of life. But gender disabilities and discriminations are found in India even today. The paradoxical situation has such that she was sometimes concerned as Goddess and at other times merely as slave.

Women in India

Now the women in India enjoy a unique status of equality with the men as per constitutional and legal provision. But the Indian women have come a long way to achieve the present positions. First, gender inequality in India can be traced back to the historic days of Mahabharata when Draupadi was put on the dice by her husband as a commodity. History is a witness that a woman was made to dance both in private and public places to please the man. Secondly, in Indian society, a female was always dependent on male members of the family even last few years ago. Thirdly, a female was not allowed to speak with loud voice in the presence of elder members of her in-laws. In the family, every fault had gone to her and responsible. Forth, as a widow her dependence on male members of the family still more increase. In many social activities she is not permitted to mix with other members of the family. Other hand, she has very little share in political, social and economic life of the society.

The early twenty century, it was rise of the National Movement under the leadership of Mahatma Gandhi who was in favor of removing all the disabilities of women. At the same time, Raja Ram Mohan Rai, Iswar Chandra Vidyasagar and various other social reformers laid stress on women's education, prevention of child marriage, withdrawals of evil practice of sati, removal of polygamy etc. The National Movement and various reform movements paved the way for their liberations from the social evils and religious taboos. In this context, we may write about the Act of Sati (abolish)

1829, Hindu Widow Remarriage Act' 1856, the Child Restriction Act, 1929, Women Property Right Act, 1937 etc.

After independence of India, the constitution makers and the national leaders recognized the equal social position of women with men. The Hindu Marriage Act, 1955 has determined the age for marriage, provided for monogamy and guardianship of the mother and permitted the dissolution of marriage under specific circumstances. Under the Hindu Adoptions and Maintenance Act, 1956, an unmarried women, widow or divorcee of sound mind can also take child in adoption. Similarly, the Dowry Prohibition Act of 1961 says that any person who gives, takes, or abets the giving or taking of dowry shall be punished with imprisonment, which may extend to six months or fine up to Rs.5000/ or with both. The Constitution of India guarantees equality of sexes and in fact grants special favors to women. These can be found in three articles of the constitution. Article 14 says that the government shall not deny to any person equality before law or equal protection of the law. Article 15 declares that government shall not discriminate against any citizen on the ground of sex. Article 15 (3) makes a special provision enabling the state to make affirmative discriminations in favor of women. Article 42 directs the state to make provision for ensuring just and human conditions of work and maternity relief. Above all, the constitution regards a fundamental duty on every citizen through Articles 15 (A), (E) to renounce the practices derogatory to the dignity of women.

Empowerment of women in India

The concept of empowerment flows from the power. It is vesting where it does not exist or exist inadequately. Empowerment of women would mean equipping women to be economically independent, self-reliant, have positive esteem to enable them to face any difficult situation and they should be able to participate in development activities. The empowered women should be able to participate in the process of decision making. In India, the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD 1985) and the National Commission for Women (NCW) have been worked to safeguard the rights and legal entitlement of women. The 73rd & 74th Amendments (1993) to the constitution of India have provided some special powers to women that for reservation of seats(33%), whereas the report HRD as March 2002, shows that the legislatures with the highest percentage of women are, Sweden 42.7%, Denmark 38%, Finland 36% and Iceland 34.9%. In India 'The New Panchayati Raj ' is the part of the effort to empower women at least at the village level.

The government of India has ratified various international conventions and human rights instruments committing to secure equal rights to women. These are CEDAW (1993), the Mexico Plan of Action (1975), the Nairobi Forward Looking Strategies (1985), the Beijing Declaration as well as the platform for Action (1995) and other such instruments. The year of 2001 was observed as the year of women's empowerment. During the year, a landmark document has been adopted, ' the National Policy for the empowerment of women.' For the beneficiaries of the women, the government has been adopted different schemes and programs i.e. the National Credit Fund for Women (1993), Food and Nutrition Board (FNB), Information and Mass Education (IME) etc.

The most positive development lasts few years has been the growing involvement of women in the Panchayati Raj institutions. There are many elected women representatives at the village council level. At present all over India, there are total 20, 56, 882 laces Grama Panchayat Members, out of this women members is 8, 38, 244 (40.48%), while total Anchalik Panchayat Members is 1, 09, 324, out of this women members is 47, 455, (40.41%) and

total Zilla Parishat members is 11, 708, out of this women members is 4, 923 (42.05%). At the central and state levels too women are progressively making a difference. Today we have seen women chief ministers, women president, different political parties' leader, well establish businessmen etc. The most notable amongst these are Mrs. Pratiba Devi Singh Patil, Shila Dexit, Mayawati, Sonia Gandhi, Brinda Karat, Nazma Heptulla, Indira Nuye (pepsi-co), Sushma Swaraj, Mamata Banarji, Medhapatekar, Indian Iron Woman, EX-prime minister Indira Gandhi so on. Women are also involving in human development issues of child rearing, education, health, and gender parity. Many of them have gone into the making and marketing of a range of cottage products-pickles, tailoring, embroidery etc. The economic empowerment of women is being regarded these days as a sine-quo-non of progress for a country; hence, the issue of economic empowerment of women is of paramount importance to political thinkers, social thinkers and reformers.

Reasons for the empowerment of women

Today we have noticed different Acts and Schemes of the central government as well as state government to empower the women of India. But in India women are discriminated and marginalized at every level of the society whether it is social participation, political participation, economic participation, access to education, and also reproductive healthcare. Women are found to be economically very poor all over the India. A few women are engaged in services and other activities. So, they need economic power to stand on their own legs on par with men. Other hand, it has been observed that women are found to be less literate than men. According to 2001 census, rate of literacy among men in India is found to be 76% whereas it is only 54% among women. Thus, increasing education among women is of very important in empowering them. It has also noticed that some of women are too weak to work. They consume less food but work more. Therefore, from the health point of view, women folk who are to be weaker are to be made stronger. Another problem is that workplace harassment of women. There are so many cases of rape, kidnapping of girl, dowry harassment, and so on. For these reasons, they require empowerment of all kinds in order to protect themselves and to secure their purity and dignity.

To sum up, women empowerment cannot be possible unless women come with and help to self-empower themselves. There is a need to formulate reducing feminized poverty, promoting education of women, and prevention and elimination of violence against women.

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CENTRE-STATE RELATIONS

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Introduction

The Constitution of India, being federal in structure, divides all powers Legislative, administration and financial between the centre and state. However there is no division of judicial power as the constitution has established an integrated judicial system to enforce both the central law as well as state laws. Though centre and the states are supreme in their respective fields, the maximum harmony and coordination between them is essential for effective operations of the federal system. Hence constitution contains elaborate provisions to regulate the various dimensions of the relations between the centre and states.

Centre State relations constitute core of federalism in India and play a vital role in the political sphere of India. Centre State Relations are following **three types**:

1. Legislative Relations contained in Part XI Articles 245 to 255
2. Administrative Relations contained in Part XI Articles 256 to 263
3. Financial Relations contained in Part XII Articles 268 to 293

Legislative Relations

Articles 245 to 255 of the deal with the legislative relation between the Centre and the States. There are four aspects of the legislative relationships between the Centre and the States which are as follows:

Territorial Extent of Central and State Legislation

Ability to pass legislation that covers all or a portion of India's territory belongs to the Parliament. Laws can be passed by the State legislature that is applicable to entire State or only a portion of it. Unless there is a sufficient connection between State and the object, State laws are not applicable outside of the State. The only body with the power to pass extraterritorial legislation is Parliament.

Distribution of Legislative Subjects

Union List, State List, and Concurrent List are three divisions established by the Constitution of India. Parliament is the exclusive authority when it comes to the **Union list**. In most cases, the State legislature alone has the power to pass legislation pertaining to the things on the **State list**. The State and Central governments can both pass laws on the subjects mentioned in the **Concurrent list**.

Parliamentary Legislation in the State Field

When Rajya Sabha approves a resolution with support of two-thirds of the members present and voting, it will provide Parliament with the authority to enact legislation on a state list issue that is best for the nation. When a declaration of a National emergency is in force the Parliament may pass laws on any matter covered by the state list. When the President's Rule is imposed in a state, the Parliament becomes empowered to make laws with respect to any matter in the State List. To implement International Agreements, the parliament can make laws on any matter in the state list for implementing International Treaties, agreements and conventions.

Centre's Control Over State Legislation

Specific laws established by the State legislature may be set aside by the governor for presidential consideration. They are entirely under the President's power. Bills on specified subjects listed in the State list can only be filed in the State legislature with the President's prior consent. For instance,

interstate trade and commerce. The President may ask a state to lay aside money bills and other financial bills for his consideration in the case of a financial emergency.

Administrative Relations

For successful working of the federal system it is desirable that there should be maximum co-operation and co-ordinations between the central and state government. Fully conscious of this fact the framers of the constitution include detailed provisions in the constitution to avoid clashes between the centre and the states. They made provision for meeting all types of eventualities arising due to difference of opinion between the sets of government. In the interest of national interest the centre was given extensive powers to direct and control the administrative affairs of the state during normal times and extra-ordinary control over the state affairs during emergency.

Articles 256 to 263 deal with the administrative relation between the Centre and States.

Delegation of Union Functions :- With the consent of the state Government the president may entrust to the officers of the state any functions in respect of any subject over which the executive power of the Union extends. Thus the states may be converted into agents of the Union Government.

All-India Service:- The presence of All-India services like the IAS and IPS, further makes the authority of the Central Government dominant over the state. The members of the All-India services are appointed by the president on the basis of a competitive examination held by the U.P.S.C

Inter-State Comity :- The constitution vests the President with the powers to establish an Inter-state council. The council may be charged with the duty to inquire into the dispute or make recommendations on inter-state dispute or matters in which some or all the states, or the Union and one or more of the states, have a common interest.

Inter-state council:- The constitution authorities the president to establish inter-state council to effect necessary co-ordination between states, in the public interest.

National Emergency:- During the national emergency the federal structure is transformed into a unitary one and all the executive authority of the state is exercised by the Union. Inter-state commerce commission:- The constitution empowers the parliament to establish such authority as it considers for enforcing the provisions of the constitution with regard to inter-state trade and commerce and confers on it such duties as it thinks fit.

The Obligation of States and the Centre

The Constitution of India has placed two restrictions on the executive power of the states in order to give ample scope to the centre for exercising its executive power in an unrestricted manner. The State's executive branch must act in a way that ensures the laws established by Parliament are upheld.

Matters where the Centre can Direct the State

Construction and maintenance of communication systems deemed to be of national or military importance by the government. Actions to be taken to guarantee the State's railways are safe. Provision of enough resources for students from linguistic minority groups to receive elementary school instruction in their home tongue. The creation and execution of specific initiatives for the ST's welfare in the various states.

Integrated Judicial System

Despite its dual polity, India has built an integrated judicial system. This unified judicial system is in charge of enforcing both Central and State laws.

Financial Relations

It is a normal feature of federations that there must be complete division of the financial resources between the centre and the federating units. In addition to their independent financial sources, the state depend on contributions and subsidies from the central government.

Articles 268 to 293 deal with the Financial Relations between the Centre and the States.

Allocation of Taxing Power

Taxation of the subjects on the Union list is the sole responsibility of Parliament. Taxation on the things included in the State list may only be done by the State legislature. The items on the concurrent list are subject to taxation by both the State and the Union.

Restriction Placed by the Constitution of India on Taxation Power of the State

A State legislature can impose taxes on profession, trades, callings and employments. A State can impose taxes on the sale or purchase of goods. But this power of state to impose sales tax is subjected to the following restrictions. No tax can be imposed on the sale or purchase of things taking place:

Out side the states

In the course of import or export; or in the course of inter-state trade and commerce. No tax can be imposed on the sale or purchase. A tax imposed on the sale or purchase of goods declared by Parliament to be of special importance in inter-state trade and commerce is subject to the restrictions and conditions specified by Parliament.

The State cannot impose a tax on the sale of electricity when it is consumed by the centre or operation of any railway by the centre or sold to the railway company for the same purpose. The State can impose tax on the sale of water or electricity sold to an authority established by Parliament for regulating or developing an Inter-state river. However, such imposition can be undertaken through a law which has received the assent of the President.

Distribution of Tax Revenues

Article 268: Taxes levied by the Centre, but they are collected and used by the State. E.g. Stamp Duties.

Article 269: Taxes are levied and collected by the Centre but assigned to the States. E.g. Taxes on the sale or purchase of goods.

Article 270: Taxes are levied and collected by the Centre but distributed between the Centre and the States. This category includes all taxes except those mentioned above, surcharges and cess. E.g. Taxes on Income.

Distribution of Non-Tax Revenues

The receipts from the following form the major sources of non-tax revenues of the Centre Posts and telegraphs, Railways, Banking, Broadcasting, Coinage and currency, Central public sector enterprise, Escheat and lapse. The receipts from the following form the major sources of non-tax revenues of the States. Irrigation, Forests, Fisheries, State public sector enterprise and Escheat and lapse

Grants-in-Aid to the States

The Constitution of India provides grants-in-aid to the State from the Central resources. Following are the two types of grants-in-aid:

Statutory Grants:

Article 275 of the empowers the Parliament to make grants to the States which are in need of financial assistance and not to every State. These sums can be different for different States. These sums are charged on the Consolidated Fund of India every year. These are given to the states based on the recommendation of the Finance Commission.

Discretionary Grants:

Article 282 of the empowers both the Centre and the States to make any grants for any public purpose, even if it is not within their legislative competence. The Centre is under no obligation to give these grants and the matter lies within its discretion.

During Financial emergency:- During the Proclamation of Financial the president can suspend the provisions relating to the division of the taxes between the union and the states and the states and grants-in-aid to the states. When such a proclamations is made the states are left only with revenue available under the state list. Moreover during such a proclamations the Union government has the powers to give directions to the states.

Control by the comptroller and auditor general on India :- The comptroller and auditor general who is responsible for the maintenance and audit of Union and state accounts is an official the central government.

Finance Commission. The President is empowered by the constitution to appoint a Finance Commission every fifth year to recommend distribution between the Union and States of the net proceeds of taxes and allocation between the States of the respective shares .Consolidated Fund of India make recommendation on any other matter in the interest of sound finance.

R.S.Sarkaria Commission was set up in June 1983 by the central government of India. Its charter was to examine the relationship and balance of power between state and central government in the country and suggest changes within the framework of constitution of India.

Conclusion :- The growing role which the regional political parties are playing at the centre has brought about perceptible changes in the centre-state relations. It has not only resulted in greater autonomy for the states, but also encouraged the states to take policy decisions, which they could not do under the earlier conditions. The presence of various bodies like National Integration council, National Development Council and Inter-State Council have exercised a profound influence on the working of the federal system.

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WOMEN'S POLITICAL PARTICIPATION: IDENTITY, REPRESENTATION, AND BARRIERS IN INDIAN DEMOCRACY

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Abstract

Women's political participation in India is a vital aspect of its democratic development, yet it remains constrained by numerous social, structural, and institutional barriers. This paper explores the dynamics of gender, identity, and representation within Indian politics, focusing on the challenge's women face in securing meaningful participation and leadership roles. Despite constitutional guarantees and legislative efforts like the Women's Reservation Bill, women's representation in political institutions, particularly at the state and national levels, remains limited. The study examines historical milestones in women's political engagement, the impact of reservation policies, and the role of local governance in empowering women through Panchayati Raj institutions. Key barriers, such as deeply ingrained patriarchal norms, socio-economic disparities, and a lack of political support, continue to hinder women's full participation. Additionally, the study highlights the intersectional challenges faced by women from marginalized communities, including caste and religion, further complicating their access to political power. Through a review of electoral data and case studies of women leaders, the paper assesses both the progress made and the persistent gender inequalities in Indian politics. It concludes with recommendations for creating a more equitable political landscape, emphasizing the need for systemic reforms, education, and greater political will to ensure women's sustained representation in governance.

Keywords: *Women's political participation, Gender representation, Indian democracy, Political inclusion, Women's Reservation Bill, Patriarchy and politics, Electoral politics, Gender equality, Barriers to political participation, Political empowerment*

Introduction

Women's political participation is a critical aspect of democracy, reflecting the extent to which a society values equality and inclusiveness. In India, a nation marked by its diverse social fabric and complex political landscape, the journey toward achieving gender parity in politics is both significant and challenging. Despite constitutional guarantees and progressive laws, women continue to face numerous obstacles that inhibit their full engagement in the political process. This article explores the historical context of women's political participation in India, the existing barriers, the role of identity and representation, and recommendations for fostering an environment that empowers women in politics.

I. Historical Context of Women's Political Participation in India:

The historical roots of women's political participation in India can be traced back to the early 20th century, during the struggle for independence. Women like Sarojini Naidu, Kamala Nehru, and others played pivotal roles in the national movement, advocating for both independence and gender equality. Naidu, for instance, was not only a prominent figure in the freedom struggle but also served as the first woman governor of an Indian state. However, despite their

contributions, the post-independence period did not translate into immediate political empowerment for women.

In 1950, the Indian Constitution was adopted, granting equal rights to all citizens, including women. Articles 14, 15, and 16 of the Constitution provided a framework for gender equality, prohibiting discrimination based on sex and guaranteeing equal opportunity in matters of public employment. Despite these provisions, the socio-cultural realities often overshadowed legal guarantees. Traditional gender roles and patriarchal norms continued to restrict women's mobility and participation in public life.

II. **Legislative Measures and Progress:**

The introduction of the 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments in 1993 marked a significant milestone in enhancing women's representation in politics, particularly at the grassroots level. These amendments mandated the reservation of one-third of seats for women in local bodies, such as Panchayati Raj institutions (PRIs) and urban local bodies. As a result, millions of women entered the political arena for the first time, bringing issues pertinent to their communities to the forefront of political discourse.

The Women's Reservation Bill, introduced in Parliament in 2008, aimed to reserve 33% of seats for women in the Lok Sabha and state legislative assemblies. While the bill faced significant political hurdles and has not yet been enacted, it sparked national conversations about women's representation in politics. The ongoing debate reflects both a growing recognition of the need for gender parity and the persistent resistance to implementing structural changes.

III. **Current State of Women's Political Participation:**

Despite the progress made through legislative measures, women's representation in Indian politics remains disproportionately low. As of 2023, women occupy approximately 14% of seats in the Lok Sabha, significantly below the global average. The underrepresentation is even more pronounced in state assemblies, where women constitute less than 10% of members in many states. This disparity highlights a critical gap in political representation and underscores the challenges women face in ascending the political ladder.

The reasons behind this underrepresentation are multifaceted, encompassing socio-cultural, economic, and political factors.

IV. **Barriers to Women's Political Participation"**

1. **Patriarchal Norms and Societal Attitudes:**

Deeply entrenched patriarchal values continue to influence perceptions of women's roles in society. Traditional norms often confine women to domestic spheres, discouraging them from participating in politics. Social stigma surrounding women in leadership positions persists, leading to a lack of support from families and communities.

2. **Economic Disparities:**

Economic inequalities further exacerbate the barriers to women's political participation. Many women, particularly from marginalized communities, lack the financial resources required to run for office or engage in political campaigns. Economic dependence on male family members often restricts their political agency and decision-making power.

3. **Political Party Dynamics:**

Political parties play a crucial role in shaping the political landscape. Unfortunately, many parties lack internal policies promoting gender equality. Women are often underrepresented in

party leadership roles, and their contributions are frequently overshadowed by male counterparts. Moreover, even when women are nominated as candidates, they are often placed in constituencies perceived as "safe," limiting their chances of winning in competitive electoral races.

4. **Violence and Intimidation:**

Women politicians frequently face threats of violence and harassment, both online and offline. The fear of violence can deter women from entering politics and participating in public life. High-profile cases of violence against women leaders underscore the dangers associated with female political engagement.

5. **Educational Barriers:**

Access to education is critical for empowering women to participate in politics. However, girls from economically disadvantaged backgrounds often face barriers to education, limiting their political awareness and engagement. The lack of education not only hinders their understanding of political processes but also affects their confidence in pursuing leadership roles.

6. **Intersectionality:**

The experiences of women in politics are further complicated by factors such as caste, class, religion, and regional identity. Women from marginalized communities, including Dalits and Adivasis, face unique challenges that intersect with gender discrimination. This intersectionality results in compounded disadvantages that hinder their political participation.

V. **The Role of Identity and Representation:**

Identity plays a significant role in shaping women's experiences in politics. Women do not constitute a homogeneous group; their experiences are shaped by various identities, including caste, religion, region, and socio-economic status. Understanding these complexities is essential for addressing the barriers women face in political participation.

Representation matters not only for women's rights but also for the broader democratic process. Women bring diverse perspectives and experiences to governance, leading to more inclusive and responsive policies. Research has shown that when women are involved in decision-making processes, issues such as health care, education, and social welfare receive greater attention. Moreover, the presence of women in leadership positions can inspire younger generations to engage in politics, breaking the cycle of underrepresentation. Role models are essential for fostering a culture of political participation among women, encouraging them to aspire for leadership roles.

VI. **Successful Case Studies:**

Despite the challenges, there are notable success stories of women who have made significant strides in Indian politics. Leaders like Mamata Banerjee, Chief Minister of West Bengal, and Jayalalithaa, the late Chief Minister of Tamil Nadu, have demonstrated that women can occupy high offices and influence political discourse. Their leadership has not only challenged traditional norms but has also inspired many women to engage in politics.

Additionally, grassroots movements led by women have proven successful in addressing local issues and advocating for policy changes. Women-led self-help groups (SHGs) have emerged as powerful platforms for economic empowerment and political engagement, allowing women to collectively address their needs and assert their rights.

VII. Recommendations for Enhancing Women's Political Participation:

To foster a more inclusive political environment for women in India, several measures can be implemented:

1. Strengthening Legislative Measures:

The government must prioritize the passage of the Women's Reservation Bill to ensure that women have a guaranteed presence in legislative bodies. This legislative change can serve as a catalyst for broader reforms in gender representation.

2. Political Party Reforms:

Political parties should implement internal quotas for women in leadership positions and candidate nominations. Training programs for women within political parties can help build their political skills and confidence.

3. Supportive Infrastructure:

Establishing mentorship programs for aspiring women politicians can provide them with guidance and support in navigating the political landscape. Providing resources, including financial support for campaign efforts, can also empower women to run for office.

4. Education and Awareness Campaigns:

Investing in educational programs that promote political literacy among women can enhance their understanding of political processes and rights. Awareness campaigns targeting communities can help challenge patriarchal norms and encourage support for women in politics.

5. Addressing Violence and Intimidation:

Robust measures must be implemented to ensure the safety of women in politics. This includes legal protection against violence and harassment, as well as creating supportive networks for women who face intimidation.

6. Promoting Intersectionality:

Policies aimed at increasing women's political participation must consider the unique challenges faced by women from marginalized communities. Tailored programs that address these intersectional issues can foster greater inclusivity in political processes.

Conclusion

Women's political participation is essential for a robust and representative democracy. While India has made significant strides in promoting gender equality through legal frameworks and grassroots initiatives, persistent barriers continue to limit women's engagement in politics. Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach that encompasses legislative reforms, political party dynamics, education, and community support. By fostering an inclusive political environment and empowering women to participate actively in governance, India can move closer to realizing its democratic ideals of equality and representation for all. The journey toward gender parity in politics is ongoing, but with sustained efforts and collective action, a more equitable political landscape can be achieved, benefiting not only women but society as a whole.

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WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH WOMEN SELF HELP GROUPS – AN ANALYSIS**Bharathi M.T***M.A, M.Phil, Faculty. Dept. of Political Science, Government first grade college, kadur*

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From the time immemorial women have been considered as a weaker section of the society and they were oppressed in several ways from enjoying the rights on a par with men. Among other things, women have been denied property rights, voting rights and right to work on a par with men for a very long period. As such, several special enactments have been passed to confer these rights on women. However, there is a gender discrimination in many countries, regions and communities which are unfavourable to women. The inherent nature of the society in general is to keep women away from active involvement in the participation of political affairs, economic affairs and social activities because women were considered resourceless in terms of money, material and managerial ability, and as such women were incapable of managing trade and other activities.

Single woman cannot come out of the house due to social reasons and to be entrepreneurs. Women are in need of skill development, managerial empowerment, financial empowerment and leadership qualities. So, a social movement in the form of women self-help groups [Here after referred to as WSHGs] were sponsored and promoted by Government at the grass-root level. Banks have been directed by Government to provide financial assistance to WSHGs and Government departments have been directed to give technical and skill development assistance to WSHGs. The WSHGs and bank linkages Programme has emerged as the major micro-finance in our country in recent years.

As the maximum number of women in a single WSHG should not exceed 20 and any number of WSHGs can be formed in a Village or a Town, all women are given opportunities to join WSMGs in their choice in a group but not in more than one WSHG. Irrespective of the caste, creed, religion, colour, region, educational status, economic status, social status, political affiliation and other discrimination, a woman can join a self-help group. Nearly half of Indian Population is women and hence there are possibilities for lakhs and lakhs of WSHGs. The role of these WSHGs in developing women will certainly develop India. Hence, it will be quite interesting to undertake a separate study to assess and examine the role of WSHGs in empowering women managerially, financially and socially.

WSHGs are a novel and innovative organizational set up in India for the women upliftment and welfare. All women in India are given chance to join any one of the WSHGs for training and development, so as to be prospective entrepreneurs and skilled workers. The WSHGs are promoted by the Government as if women in India may not be resourceful enough to be entrepreneurs. When the WSHGs arrange training facilities to carry out certain kind of work which are suitable for women in India, banks must arrange financial assistance to carry out manufacturing and trading activities, arranging marketing facilities while the Government will procure the products of WSHGs, arrange for enhancing the capacity of women in terms of leadership quality and arranging for the management of WSHGs by themselves so as to have administrative capability. As a social movement with Government support, WSHGs become more or less a part and parcel of the society.

The number of women in a single WSHG is small. All members may not be educated and may not have sufficient background to carry on tiny industries and trade. Under these circumstances, it is believed that WSHGs will enhance women empowerment managerially, financially, and socially. As

the WSHGs are of recent origin and there is mushroom growth of WSHGs all over India, all the state Governments and Government of India are interested in

Table-1 - Sample Size

Taluk	Members	Sample (0.25%)	Actual Sample
Chitrdurga	43722	109	95
Hiriyur	24151	60	55
Chalkere	23536	59	55
Holalekere	41869	105	95
Total	133278	333	300
(Source: Primary data)			

organizing WSHGs with the objective that WSHGs will empower women. Therefore a need arises to reexamine empirically whether the Government sponsored and public financial Institutions financial assistance supported WSHGs really empower women of India or not.

Significance of The Study: Men

and women are equal before the Constitution of India, Besides women are considered as a privileged class by means of several central and state legislations. In principle, all the political parties of India have agreed to give one-third exclusive reservation for women in political participation, one third reservation in admissions in educational institutions and job opportunities. The Karnataka state Government have passed an Act to give co-parcenership right in properties to women. Women are also a privileged class in obtaining financial assistances for starting industries with one per cent concessional rate of interest.

In Karnataka the women Development Board has been set up for the welfare of women. In spite of these arrangements, women are considered as a weaker section of the society as they are considered as if they are not resourceful financially, managerially and socially. Most women in rural areas of India are uneducated, poor, unskilled, non participatory in economic activity and non-involvement in the economic development of India with the inherent nature of accepting male domination and decision. Women are not allowed to act with economic independence, self-reliance and independent decision-making and thinking. The resourcelessness among the poor and uneducated women may be the cause for economic dependence. As such, a social movement by name WSHGs are promoted with the objectives of empowering women in the economic, managerial and social fields. Organization of WSHGs are a few years old and hence it may be considered significant by means of a separate study to examine the empowerment of women through WSHGs quantitatively and qualitatively by means of field-survey, research, analysis and interpretation.

Objectives

WSHGs are novel organizations at the grass root level to bring a socio-economic transformation to women of India. There is scope for every women to join WSHGs and to have empowerment economically, managerially, financially, socially and what not. As such, the objectives of the proposed study are to re-examine the empowerment of women by having joined the WSHGs.

1. To re-examine the rationale behind women empowerment,
2. To review the role of Government for the uplift of women,
3. To examine the role of WSHGs for the empowerment of women on principle and.

4. To examine empirically the empowerment of women managerially, financially and socially by having joined WSHGs.

Sampling Design

Proportionate stratified random sampling technique was adapted. In the study district there are four taluks and the respondents were taken from all the four taluks. The details of sample taken are shown in Table-1 for analysis. Convenient -sampling method was followed in taking samples from the taluks.

Around 0.25% of samples were considered for the study. On the first phase, a sample of 109 from Chitradurga, 60 from Hiriur, 59 from Challakere and 105 from Holalekere were considered. However, the responses were got only from 95 respondents from Chitradurga 55 from Hiriur, 55 from Challakere and 95 from Holalekere

Methodology

Statistical survey method of research was followed. The survey was conducted on the women self-help groups of Chitradurga district of Karnataka. The researcher visited every village of Chitradurga district. There are about 1400 villages in Chitradurga district and there are about 8156 WSHGs as on 2006 in Chitradurga district. From out of 8156 groups 300 respondents were chosen at random. The sample size is decided at the convenience of the researcher as the population size is larger. The researcher met the respondents with a Kannada [vernacular language] version of the question scheduled to the respondent to fill up the question schedule as per reply given by respondents. The statistical survey research was undertaken with a view to reach certain conclusions.

Data Collection And Analysis:

Both primary and secondary data were widely used. Secondary data were collected from the records of the Government of Karnataka Revenue Department, Social Welfare Department and district records. Savings details were also collected from the WSHGs. Primary data were collected with the help of a well structured interview schedule. First a pilot study was conducted and data were collected from 40 government officials, leaders of WSHGs and senior members of WSHGs.

Research Findings

1. Majority of the respondents are Hindus.
2. Respondents represent from all social groups.
3. Younger generation shows active participation.
4. Politicians were found to be interested in bringing members to WSHGs.
5. 70 per cent are stated to be economically dependent before joining WSHGs.
6. Most of the respondents are not allowed to take financial decisions in the family matters before joining WSHGs.
7. 71.05 per cent are empowered to take financial decisions in the family after joining WSHGs.
8. 69 per cent took training in WSHGs.
9. 65 per cent started business / profession on their own after the training in WSHGs.
10. 100 per cent of the respondents are under financial constraints before joining WSHGs.
11. 80 per cent of the members were -able to overcome the financial constraints after joining WSHGs.
12. 38 per cent of the respondents felt that the financial assistance of WSHGs was inadequate.
13. 74.07 per cent felt that the new profession gave them earnings.
14. 76 per cent felt that the earnings after joining WSHGs was greater than earnings before.
15. 80 per cent of the respondents developed the art of interaction.
16. The respondents could influence the behaviour of family members, society members and members of the group.
17. Single largest group of respondents spent their income for family maintenance.
18. Most of the respondents became earning members.
19. Most members became politically affiliated.
20. 80 per cent of the respondent agreed that they were empowered and
21. 85 per cent of the respondents could solve their personal problems.

Suggestions

1. Even after having joined WSHGs forty per cent of the respondents felt that they were economically dependent. As such, a separate research may be under taken to examine the reasons for economic dependency of members of WSHGs. When the reasons for the economic dependency are known, it may be possible to assure economic independency to the members.
2. Even after having joined WSHGs twenty per cent of the members were under financial constraints to do business or profession. Therefore, measures may be taken by the WSHGs themselves in their weakly meeting asking the members about their financial constraints for doing business and the constrains may be avoided either from internal sources or from obtaining financial assistance from the public financial institutions.
3. The members of the WSHGs may be encouraged to do business from the skill developed through WSHGs.
4. Politicians were to be interested in bringing members to WSHGs and most members became politically affiliated. This is not a welcome move. Because, WSHGs will become outfits of political organizations. Further WSHGs may be brought under the domination of political parties. As such a moral suasion may be popularized by saying that WSHGs are non-political organization. Hence political interference to be avoided.

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YOUTH PARTICIPATION IN POLITICS: PROMOTING THE ROLE OF YOUTH IN POLITICAL AND DEMOCRATIC SPACES

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Abstract

Participation and contribution of all people in formal political processes is essential for all democratic nations across the globe. Young people are the future of any democracy. Today's youths are tomorrow's leaders, and they can already bring new ideas to solve the world's complications. However, young people continue to be harshly under-represented in assembly. Youth political participation is taking place within a context of self-governing transformation, including a global decline in the state of democracy, dwindling space for civic society, polarisation of the political and social space, economic crisis and precarity, swift digitalisation, the effect of the Covid-19 pandemic and, most recently, war. In this setting, we are witnessing a lack of trust in political institutions, an increasing disengagement from the political system and a decline in youth participation in institutional politics. Young people's participation is crucial for shaping and transforming democracies. This Youth Knowledge article reminds us that while the context might be changing, young people's participation is crucial for shaping and transforming democracies. Youth political participation, citizenship and relationship with democracy remain a multifaceted theme for youth research, policy and practice. While this paper does not claim to answer all the questions or represent the realities of all young people across the country, but tries to give a sight into the landscape of youth engagement in a changing world, highlighting realities, trends and main issues.

Introduction

Youth participation in political, social and economic life is crucial for a healthy democracy. And youth participation has been at the core of working processes within the youth segment. Advanced by the different angles of the youth trio, youth participation continues to be one of the most important policy priorities, while research dedicates widespread resources in trying to understand the new forms of youth political participation. At grass-roots level, youth organisations and youth workers are still struggling to find gears and gadgets to inspire youth participation, while working with young people on including them as actors on the political participation scene.

In the youth sector, when analysing political participation, the framework is mainly defined through what we know about “visible” youth political participation. We know that voting or participation in political parties’ activities or participation in youth or regional/national parliaments and assemblies are still the most popular forms of youth political participation. The Youth Partnership defines political participation broadly as “any activity that shapes, affects, or involves the political sphere”. Subsequently, in policy and research, we are still looking for the spaces and contexts where young people have a voice in influencing decisions that affect their lives, politics, relationships, or active engagement of young people in their communities.

Three typologies of political participation

- Conventional/traditional political participation: This includes institutionalised activities taking place in the democratic arena, such as voting, standing in elections or becoming a member of a political party, youth organisation or youth or student council.
- Unconventional/alternative political participation activities which aims at persuading the political domain but are carried out via different means than the narrow avenue of conventional

participation, activities which use out-of-the-system approaches to achieve their goals like youth movements, demonstrations, strikes, boycotts or petitions, etc.

- Individualised political participation often takes place at the individual level and as such does not require group, community or mass action. It is mainly linked to activities of the individual, activities that carry a political meaning in various areas, such as animal welfare, or ethical aspects of the production processes (Bárta and Lavizzari 2021, Salto Participation and Information 2022).

Political Attitudes of the Youth

The country like India desperately needs some young leaders and, we feel that the system needs to be reformed but we don't want to take the responsibility on our shoulders. In our country the chief posts are mostly occupied by the politicians above 50 years of age this should be get changed. Youths should build a foundation now for a prosperous future, if we want to see a better India, it is time to take responsibility. Except youth feel anxious and gets involved in politics at all stages, we cannot anticipate a nation to grow. The youth of this nation are in the need of platforms which help them uplift themselves to the level of political appreciation. They need mentorship and guidance which helps them to project their spirit of development and represent the largest age group of the country.

When we see the literature on political participation, contributions to the field of political attitudes have also broadened our understanding of how political attitudes develop and how the political attitudes of young adults differ from those of adults. This paper takes the different approaches to socialization and the debated inputs from other fields and focuses on development, maturation, and the stability of attitudes in order to answer how young adults develop political attitudes.

Hyman (1959, p. 25) thought of political socialization as an individual's "learning of social patterns corresponding to his societal positions as mediated through various agencies of society." Considering that it is one of the most commonly used definitions of political socialization, it is surprising that researchers had mostly analysed family influence first and foremost and neglected various agencies of society. Furthermore, Sapiro (2004) points out that, in its early days, dedicated research on political socialization (Easton et al., 1969; Searing et al., 1973; Jennings and Niemi, 1974) mostly focused on shared party affiliations, participation in voluntary organizations, or the genuine political interest of children and their parents' possible influence on it.

However, scholars have repeatedly faced the same methodological challenge, since young children do not possess many issue beliefs at all (Searing et al., 1973). This makes it hard to identify inferences valuable to political science. Hess and Torney-Purta (1967), on the other hand, claim that children are able to express political opinions and partisanship.

Reasons for lack of participation of youth in the electoral process

- Apathetic attitude towards the political system
- Disenchantment with politics and politician
- Increasing alienation of the youth in the recent years due to technology and electronic gadgets
- Relation of political participation in general and of youth in particular with the issues related to the basic electoral system
- While youth can vote when they are 18 yrs but cannot be voted i.e. can't contest till, they are 25 yrs for Lok Sabha and State Assembly
- Lack of democratic political activities in the colleges/universities
- Migration of youth for education, and problem associated with inclusion of names in the electoral roll.

Guiding Principles

Some of the core principle for meaningful and effective youth political participation are listed below

- **Youth friendly, relevant and purposeful:** Activities to enhance youth political participation should be as youth-driven as possible. Young people themselves can decide on their priorities, methods, and tactics. The environment and working methods can be adapted to youth capacities and needs – meeting youth where they're at. Depending on the target age group and context, activities might focus on, among other options: informal, results-oriented projects; low access barriers; easy language; being issue-driven; being competitive with a game element; or technology if educated youth are targeted
- **Inclusive:** Ensuring all young people are able to participate, regardless of age, background, religion, gender, race/ethnicity, sexual orientation, ability, geography, and mental health. This requires an acceptance and embracing of diversity, and efforts to build upon young people's diversity and experiences. Appropriate methods can be applied to give marginalized groups of youth equal chances to participate. This also requires being sensitive to gender dynamics and power relationships. Being inclusive requires the removal of barriers, including economic barriers, to enable youth engagement.
- **Flexible and open to innovation:** Commitment of youth and adults working with youth to be open to new ideas and have a willingness to take risks and challenge existing established processes and structures.
- **Capacity-developing:** Strengthen youth agency by supporting capacity development for young people, youth organizations, networks, and movements, to enhance mutual responsiveness, trust, and collaboration.

Additionally, the following measures can improve Youth Involvement

- Special campaign at least one month before the claims and Objections
- Using Youth as volunteers to register others in electoral rolls
- Involvement of the Colleges including the teachers and NSS, NCC
- Social networking sites such as Facebook, Orkut and twitter
- Special website for Youth by ECI that can have all information pertaining to electoral process. Slogan writing, Elocution, Painting Competitions, in Schools, Colleges and Universities

Use of mass media and Folk Media

- FM radio, Popular TV Channels/programmes
- News papers
- Uploading videos on YouTube and other social medium
- Puppet, Street play, Folk songs, Folk theatre

Social media and other online resources are key tools in enhancing youth participation and helping to educate young people on civic values, as young people are already highly active on and familiar with these platforms. However, online communications also come with the risks brought by inauthentic content, so it is important that countries pair online communications efforts with transparency and other countermeasures against mis- and disinformation

EVM Training

- To be available in the College
- Mock polls in the Colleges

- Media campaign emphasizing that EVMs are tamper proof and also emphasizing that secrecy of Ballot is maintained
- Involving Students in this campaign

Voter Education through Intensive IEC Activities

- Sustain Voter Education Campaign at National and State Level
- Professional media agencies to be engaged to make appropriate campaign messages to impart knowledge and even look beyond knowledge aspect to bring about a desired change in the attitude and sustain the campaign till the election day to translate this increased knowledge and changed attitude into a responsible voting behaviour
- This campaign should be spearheaded by ECI, at National and State levels
- Election machinery should mainly see that the Registration is done properly, Electoral rolls are error free and the pre poll preparations are good enough to build confidence of voters in the whole Poll Process - its neutrality and fairness

The Constitutional Mandate

- Article 326 of the Constitution (as after the 61 amendments in March 1989) provides for all those over 18 years of age to vote.
- The Statement of Objects and Reasons said: ``The present-day youth are literate and enlightened and the lowering of the voting age would provide to the unrepresented youth of the country an opportunity to give vent to their feelings and help them become a part of the political process. The present-day youth are very much politically conscious. It is, therefore, proposed to reduce the voting age from 21 years to 18 years’’.

To analyse how youth’s make use of their power and authority as a politician

Power is one of the key concepts in the political phenomena. Power is habitually defined as the ability to influence the behaviour of others with or without resistance. Authority is often used for power perceived as legitimate by the social structure. Just in case and on the off chance of youth’s it is possible for someone to have formal authority but no power. This may occur if they are unable to exercise autonomy to make decisions or lead a specific group of people. Politics is the process by which group of people make decisions. The term is generally applied to behaviour within civil governments, but politics has been observed in all human group interactions, including corporate, academic and religious institutions. It consists of social relations involving authority and power, the regulation of political units and the methods and tactics used to formulate and apply social policy. Youths should positively make use of their power and authority as a politician. They can be a creative force, a dynamic source of innovations, and they have undoubtedly, throughout history, participated, contributed, and even catalysed important changes in political systems, power-sharing dynamics and economic opportunities.

Significance of Youth Participation in formal Political Process

For political systems to be representative, all parts of society must be included. When young people are disenfranchised or disengaged from political processes, a significant portion of the population has little or no voice or influence in decisions that affect group members’ lives. A key consequence is the undermining of political systems’ representativeness.

To make a difference in the longer term, it is essential that young people are engaged in formal political processes and have a say in formulating today’s and tomorrow’s politics. Inclusive political participation is not only a fundamental political and democratic right but also is crucial to building stable and peaceful societies and developing policies that respond to the specific needs of younger generations. For young people to be adequately represented in political institutions, processes, and

decision-making, and in particular in elections, they must know their rights and be given the necessary knowledge and capacity to participate in a meaningful way at all levels.

When there are obstacles to participating in formal, institutionalized political processes, young people can rapidly feel disempowered. Many tend to believe that their voices are not going to be heard or that they will not be taken seriously even if they are heard. The problem becomes circular as politicians may lose interest in responding to the aspirations of young people if they cannot win their votes. This in turn leads to young people being increasingly excluded from taking part in decision-making, or in debates about key socio-economic and political issues, despite their sensitivity to the demands for social equity and justice, environmental protection and cultural diversity.

In new and emerging democracies, the inclusion of young people in formal political processes is important from the start. See Annex: A Spotlight on Countries in Transition. Young people's active contributions can bring democratic values to life, leading to the overturning of authoritarian practices. In countries where young people have led protests that have forced authoritarian regimes from power, they are likely to feel significant frustration if they are not included in new formal decision-making procedures. This can destabilize democratization and accelerate conflict dynamics.

Conclusion

Youths are the future of our nation. We found that youth participation in Indian politics is very lower. To improve participation, the election commission, governments, educational institutions, the corporate sector should take some measures and there is a need to understand what determines young people's disengagement in politics. The lack of political knowledge and resources for young people within their local communities is also a source of concern for many; especially, but not exclusively for youths. Government and other non – government bodies be supposed to recognize and enhances youth's strengths and should also promote positive outcomes for young people by providing opportunities and furnishing the support needed to build on their leadership strengths. The impact that youth have on our country, towards its progress is tremendous. They shape the future of our country and lead it to the path of remarkable accomplishments. But in doing so one of the major factors that influence the development of the country is the political system of the country which the youth must also strive to lead as they must not forget that their voice matters and their participation in Indian politics makes a concrete difference provided, they stay truthful and determined to their intention without getting deviated to any kind of influence in a negative path. It is also important to remember that even small acts of engagement, such as staying informed, voting, or joining youth-led organizations, are a way to encourage yourself as a youth to the political aspect. It is very essential to promote political education, encourage open dialogue, and create platforms for youth to voice their concerns. By fostering an inclusive and supportive environment, more young individuals are inspired to actively engage and address the existing challenges by creating a more inclusive and vibrant political landscape.

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CENTRE STATES RELATIONS

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Introduction:

The Essence of Federal Government is the division of powers between Central Government and State Governments.) With in their sphere both Central and State Governments is Supreme and co-ordinate. If conflicts arise between the two Governments they are by independent Supreme Court.

The constitution of India establishes a federal form of Government. Naturally, there is a division of powers between the Central Government and State Governments. In India framers of the constitution gave lot of thought and time to the question of distribution of powers; between Centre and States. The scheme of distribution of powers is determined by the peculiar conditions prevailed at the time of framing the constitution. In the USA when 13 colonies agreed to form the Federal Government they were not ready for complete subordination to national government. They agreed to vest specified powers to National Government which are of common to all. The constitution of the USA accordingly consists of only one list of subjects. Rest of powers and residency powers remain with States. But Canadian constitutions is different. The Canadians witnessed the America Civil war and carefully watched controversy over rights of the states, they have agreed to make centre strong and vest it with more powers. The method of distribution of powers adopted by the Indian Constitution was neither American nor Canadian. It was the result of political conditions pre- vailed in India. The scheme of distribution of powers in the Indian Constitution remain the same as it was under the Government of India Act 1935.

I. Legislative Relations between the Centre and States

Seventh schedule of the constitution contains three lists, the central list, state list and concurrent list. All subjects for legislative purpose have been divided into three lists: The central list contains 97 subjects, the number now has increased to 99, the state list contains 66 subjects, the number has reduced to 61, the concurrent list consists of 47 subjects, now number has increased to 51 subjects.

The state list consists of 61 subjects which are of diversified interest. The selection of these subjects is made on the basis of local interest. Some of the important subjects are; police, public order, prisons, local- government, public health, Public Libraries and museums, Agriculture, water supply and irrigation, trade and commerce etc. The state legislature has the exclusive power of making laws over these subjects.

The concurrent List consists of 51 subjects, the subjects in which uniformity of laws throughout the country is needed, are included in this list. The list includes subjects such as; marriage and divorce; transfer of property, other than agricultural land; contracts; Civil procedure; drugs and poisons; economic and Social plan- ning, Social security Education, Labourer Welfare, Price Control etc. The parliament of India and state legislatures have concurrent power of making laws on these subjects. So long as Parliament does not pass a law on any of these subjects, the states may pass laws. But once parliament enacts on these subjects, parliament law prevails over the state law.

1) Power of Parliament to legislate with Respect to any matter in the State List in the National interest. (Article 249)

Article 249 says that, if the Raj-sabha, the upper house of the Indian Parliament declares by passing a resolution, with the support of two thirds of the members present and voting, that it is

necessary in the national interest that parliament should make laws on any subject embodied in the State List. Then, Parliament can make laws on the subject of state list. Such resolution remains valid for one year, for further continuation another resolution may be passed.

2) Power of Parliament to legislate with Respect to any matter in the State List if a Proclamation of Emergency is in operation (Article 250)

Under the Article 250; while the Proclamation of emergency is made by the President, Parliament has the power to legislate on State Subject.

3) Power of Parliament to legislate for two or more states by consent.

According to article 252, two or more State Legislatures by passing a resolution may ask Parliament to make laws on any matter in the State List.

4) Legislation for giving effect to international Agreements

According to Article 253 parliament has power to make law for the whole country for implementing any. treaty with any other country. This provision entitles the Parliament to legislate even in respect of those Subjects which are included in the State List.

5) Power of Parliament to legislate for states in case of Failure of Constitutional Machinery -

According to Article 356 if the president declare emergency in any state; and if State Legislature is dissolved during that period parliament will make Laws, on Subjects in the State List.

The entire Scheme of distribution of powers displays a Strong tendency towards centralisation. Even than; Careful Study of distribution of powers, clearly shows that, the States are not reduced to a position of in- significance.

II. Administrative Relations between the Union and the States

In a federation co-operation and co-ordination are two essential requisites for smooth and proper functioning of Administrative machinery. In federal System usually States enjoy a lot of autonomy and independence, but at the same time both should work in close harmony with each other. If centre and states work at cross purpose in administrative field, the very purpose of federation can not realise, and national unity will be at stake. Infact the success and strength of federal polity depends upon the maximum co-operation and co-ordination between two sets of Governments.

The Constitution of India has made an attempt for bringing harmonious relationship between centre and states. Framers of the constitution included detailed provisions to avoid clashes between Union and States, in administrative field. Chapter II of Part XI of the constitution is concerned with this aspect. (Article 256 to 363) In the administrative field also the Central Government has been given a dominant position.

According to (article 257 the executive powers of every state shall be so exercised such a manner that they should not violate executive powers of the Union) The central can give directions to State Governments for this purpose. The Central Government may give directions to the states for the maintenance and construction of means of Communication, which are of national and military importance. It can also give instruction to state government for the protection of railways.

- (1) Article 256 provides that executive powers of each state should be exercised as to ensure in compliance with the laws made by the Parliament.
- (2) The President may entrust to Officers of States certain executive functions of the union relating to any matter. (Article 258))
- (3) The Central Government has considerable control over administrative machinery of the State. This control is exercised through, the personnel of.

- a) All India Services, who are responsible to the centre for all their actions. The All India Services are common to the Union and the States, they are recruited by the centre. It is a means of indirect control for the centre over the state.
- b) The Governors of states who are appointed by the president and they are responsible to the president. The State Government has no control over their activities. The Governors are supposed to act as the representatives of the Central Government.
- c) The Supreme Court and High Court Judges are appointed by the President, the removal of these officials also rests with the union. Judges of the High Courts are transferred by the president from one High Court to another.
- d) The comptroller Auditor General of India appointed by the President, he and his officers are concerned not only with the accounts and auditing of the union but also those of the states.
- e) The Election Commission, is appointed by the President, it is incharge of conducting election to not only to parliament but also to the State Legislature.
- f) The Central Government has power to give grants-in-aid and loans to the States.
- (4) It is the duty of the state executive to see that all the laws made by the Parliament are duly enforced and executed. The Central Government can issue instructions to the State Government in this respect.
- (5) The parliament of India is authorised to make laws with respect to the adjudication of disputes regarding inter state river water, and boundary dispute. The Parliament provides for the Creation of a tribunal to settle the interstate river water dispute. It should be noted that the verdict of the tribunal shall be binding on the concerned states, no court shall have the power to review the judgement of the tribunal.
- (6) To facilitate smooth working of the administrative machinery of the country as a whole and to achieve better co-ordination between centre and states, the president has power to appoint inter-state council. The council will enquire into dispute and Settles the disputes. Accordingly an Interstate council was established in 1990.
- (7) The President of India is empowered to declare a state emergency in case of out break of war. During such period of emergency the central Govt. gives direction to the State Governments. the President may authorises the parliament to make laws on the subjects which cases under State-List.
- (8) Article 365 provides that if the State Government fails to carry out the directions of Central Government the Central Government regards it as a failure of constitutional machinery in that state. The President can declare a state of emergency, in that state.
- (9) Planning Commission established by the Central Government formulates five year plans for the Eco and Social development, It acts as an advisory body of the Central Government.

III. Financial Relations Between Union and States

Financial relationship is extremely complicated relationship in a federal system. The requisite of a federal government is both centre and State Government must have independent control over financial resources. Because without financial autonomy, to the states there can be no political autonomy for them.

Financial Relations

Chapters I and II of Part XII of the Constitution contain the main provisions governing the Centre-State financial relations. Distribution of revenues between the two levels of governments is specified as follows:

Article 268 says the certain duties levied by the Central government can be collected and appropriated by the States. Stamp duties and such duties of excise on medicinal and toilet preparations mentioned in the Union List are levied by the Union government and they are collected by the States.

Under Article 269 taxes on sales or purchase of goods and taxes on the consignment of goods are levied and collected by the Centre and they are assigned to the States. Parliament can formulate principles for determining when a sale or purchase of or consignment of goods takes place in the course of inter-State trade or commerce.

Article 270 speaks of taxes levied and distributed between the Centre and the States. All taxes and duties referred to in the Union List (except the duties and taxes referred to in

Articles 268 and 269) are levied and collected by the Centre and are distributed between the two levels of governments.

According to Article 271 parliament has the power to levy and collect surcharge on certain duties and taxes. This is not sharable with the States.

Article 275 provides for grants-in-aid of revenues made under a law by parliament to States in need of assistance.

Article 289 exempts the property and income of States from the Union taxation.

Conclusion: The States are overburdened with huge expenditure on payment of salaries, welfare of weaker sections, rural development, irrigation, and other vital areas of nation-building. It may be noted here that out of 61 subjects in the State List, about 15 subjects deal with development. Granting more autonomy to the States will strengthen Indian federalism. Ten regional parties of North-East formed the North-East Regional Political Front in 2013 to protect the territorial, cultural, social, political and economic rights of the region.

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POLITICAL INTEREST AND ITS INFLUENCE ON YOUTH ENGAGEMENT IN POLITICS**Pavana B S***Assistant Professor and HOD, Department of Political Science, Sree Siddaganga College of Arts, Science and Commerce for Women, Tumakuru. Mail id: pavanabs2@gmail.com*

Abstract

Politics is a more important aspect of any democracy; youths are the main pillars of the present and future of it. Youth participation become the most crucial part of politics as their interest differs significantly. This study investigates the relationship between the youth's interest in politics and their perception of the importance of political participation. The quantitative research design is used in this study; the data is collected through Google Forms from college students.

The results of Spearman's rank correlation indicate that a high correlation between interest in politics among young people and the perception of participation's importance does exist. Feeling indifference, distrust of politicians, even fear of some sort of persecution is named as the main obstacles to participation. At the same time, according to suggestions from the respondents, politics could be more accessible and appealing for young people if civic education is enhanced, there are more representatives of youth, and government transparency is increased. These insights bring home the realization that political interest needs to be developed for increasing disposition of youth to contribute toward building their communities and their future.

These results will guide policymakers, educators, and youth associations to address the barriers stopping youths from politics and create special programs that engage youths in politics. The insights of this study help to encourage young generations to participate in politics and also help them to shape the future.

Keywords: *Youth's participation, Politics, Perception on politics.*

1. Introduction

Young generation make substantial portion in India's population, who are powerful force of India's future. With the exposure of internet and media specially, social media youths' participation is there in every aspect like issues related to environment, climate, equality, social and economic issues. Young people are raising their voices in social moments and involving themselves in speaking out on issues, but we rarely see the same participation level of youths in politics. The young people involving themselves in voting, taking politics as profession, or in governance remains low. Many youths feel disconnected from the main stream politics as they feel that their opinions are less heard and their voices aren't valued. Nowadays social media has become main source of information for youth. They are influenced by the social media influencers and other dominant personalities to seek any information, so it becomes important to political parties and also education ministry to bring a programs by using social media so that the youth are can easily access to the information and include themselves in the political activities, because many youths are not even voting in elections. So it important to spread awareness about the democratic rights and duties to young generations so that they become responsible citizens in future as the future belongs to them.

This study seeks to explore the role of political interest in shaping youths' perception of their importance in politics. By examining whether an interest in politics increases the likelihood of young people's view political participation as importance. Additionally, it also studies the factors that encourage and discourage youth from participating in politics. The main objectives of this study is to assess the relationship between youth interest in politics and their perception of the importance of youth participation in politics and To identify key motivating factors and barriers affecting youth political participation.

2. Literature Review

Young individuals seek about politics from their family and friends, (Sears & Levy, 2003) explains political socialization theory which highlights adults form their opinion on politics from the society they live and interact. According to Verba, Schlozman, and Brady's approach, recruitment, incentives, and resources all have an effect on participation. For instance, young people exhibit strong political interest when they have access to information and organisational tools (Verba, Schlozman, & Brady, 1995).

Youth Empowerment theory suggests that when young people perceive their involvement as significant, it can boost their political participation (Christens & Peterson, 2012). By empowering youth, we can foster a greater sense of efficacy, which in turn makes them more inclined to engage in political activities. According to Social Identity Theory, political participation is often influenced by one's identification with certain social groups or causes, such as those related to environmental or social justice (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). Young people tend to engage more in politics when they feel a personal connection to issues that relate to their identity.

Young people experience several kinds of challenges to their engagement, including dissatisfaction with politics and bureaucratic mistrust, which may reduce their drive and perception of value. Ekman and Amnå's (2012) research underlines the psychological and institutional barriers that influence youth participation in European contexts. Youth activism nowadays primarily occurs on social media. Jenkins (2006) focusses at how these platforms assist connect young individuals with political parties and provide places for political activity. When young people believe that their participation in politics truly matters, they are more likely to do so. As stated by Norris (2003), youths who have a strong sense of empowerment and efficacy may be inspired to get involved in political systems where they believe they've got the capacity to effect change.

3. Methodology

The quantitative research method is used in this study, the survey questionnaires is used to collect the data. The sample is consisted of university students; google forms were circulated among students to get the response, out of 120 questionnaires issued 103 responses were considered for study. The questionnaire consists of demographics questions such as age, educational qualifications and Likert scale questions which consist of questions which study level of interest, frequency of discussions about politics among friends and family members, and impact of social media on political participation among youth etc. The Spearman's rank correlation is used to analyse the data using SPSS software. Interest in Politics is considered as Independent Variable and Perception of importance of youth participation is taken as dependent variable.

4. Results

Figure 1 explains the barriers which are preventing the youths to participate in politics. It is noticeable that more than 30 respondents feel that lack of interest is the barrier for them in involving in politics and more than 20 respondents fear of negative consequences from the politics, which suggest that negative impact of politics results in barrier for the youths. Even some youths feel that distrust in politicians and political parties lead them not to participate in the political activities.

Figure 1

Source: Author’s computation.

From the Figure 1 it is evident that the most prevalent barrier for youths is lack of interest in them towards the politics followed by fear of negative consequences, these responses indicate that some youths are hesitant to participate in politics due to a lack of trust in political figures and fear of potential repercussions, such as social or personal risks associated with political involvement.

Figure 2

Source: Author’s computation.

Figure 2 explains the youth desire for changes in politics which would encourage them to participate in it. Most of the youth feel that civic education in schools should be improved so that youth will be evolved in politics and are aware of political activities since school days. So enhancing the civic

education plays significant role in encouraging youths to participate in politics. Along with this, they also prefer the young people to represent themselves in political offices, suggesting that seeing young people in leadership roles might motivate others to get involved in politics. Transparency and accountability in government is also backed by some of the respondents. Other two changes i.e accessible information on political issues and candidates and platform for youth voices to be heard in policymaking have received equal importance from the respondents.

Table 1: Results of correlation

Correlations				
			How interested are you in politics?	In your opinion, how important is it for young people to participate in politics?
Spearman's rho	How interested are you in politics?	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.344**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	103	103
	In your opinion, how important is it for young people to participate in politics?	Correlation Coefficient	.344**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	103	103
**, Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				

Spearman's rho of 0.344, which signifies a moderate positive link between people's Interest in Politics, and their Perception of the Importance of Youth Participation. That means that if respondents are more interested in politics, they are also more inclined to seeing youth participation as important. Whereas this correlation is not really strong, it in fact is noteworthy and shows a trend: those who have got a considerable interest in politics are more likely to endorse youth participation in political activities. The p-value, 0.000 is highly significant on the 0.01 level, indicating that there is a minimal probability this correlation was due to random chance. It boosts the confidence of the observed association in the sample.

This suggests the results are statistically significant, meaning that the positive association between political interest and perceived importance of youth participation found in this study is unlikely to be due to chance, but rather reflect a true relationship present in the population from which our sample was drawn.

Discussion

Results could be useful for informing policy or educational interventions to promote youth political engagement. For example, political interest-increasing initiatives (such as civic education, discussion of politics among youth or directly through social media) may also increase young people's respect for their role in politics. This will also mean that due to the correlation ($\rho = 0.344$) being modest, other factors such as civic knowledge, peer effect or media exposure may also shape youth perceptions of the importance of participation. A statistically significant, moderate positive association exists between interest in politics and perceived importance of youth participation in politics. This relationship underscores the value of cultivating an interest in politics as an avenue for increasing youth participation.

and implies that efforts to increase political awareness may also be impactful on strengthening civic engagement amongst the younger population.

Conclusion

This research points out an important, yet often ignored, aspect of youth politics: youths are outspoken on the social issues, but their active participation in formal politics is still noticeably low. The results of this research indicate that there is a moderate positive relationship between interest in politics and the opinion about the significance of youth in politics. This indicates that nurturing genuine political feelings in youth may stimulate deeper political activity.

Some reasons that keep youths away from political life are distrust of politicians, fear of adverse consequences, and uninteresting subjects. In this respect, it is important to note that increasing civic education and incorporating youth-friendly political content on social media platforms will create avenues for political learning and activation. The response trends were promising in showing that increased transparency, more youths in political offices, and better accountability of government could be motivating factors for more participation.

These findings underpin the importance of educational and policy interventions that nurture among youth a sense of efficacy and responsibility. Society, through supportive frameworks that allow avenues for meaningful participation, will be assured of an informed and empowered generation contributing actively to democratic processes and governance. Future researchers can include the demographics variables to study the perception of youths so that more generalisations can be made out of results.

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DALIT ASSERTION THROUGH ELECTORAL POLITICS: VCK IN TAMIL NADU – A STUDY

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Abstract

This study discusses Dalit political claims in Tamil Nadu in relation to the Viduthalai Chiruthaigal Katchi (VCK), which distinguishes itself from other groups of Dalits in the state because of its differing approach to social and political action. Unlike several parties of Dalits, which mainly take up caste-related issues, VCK takes a broader approach by advocating full social justice, secularism, and anti-caste policies. By looking at the party's methods, electoral success, and influence on Dalit empowerment, this study highlights the important part that political involvement plays in battling caste discrimination and promoting social justice.

INTRODUCTION

The ethos of caste and the strategies for social justice have profoundly influenced the political landscape of Tamil Nadu. Dalits, often designated as Harijans, have historically endured political and socioeconomic subjugation by members of the higher castes and radical religious factions. The outcry of the Dalit community against the tyranny of the dominant caste precipitated significant movements and political transformations. Visionaries such as Iyothee Thass and Rettamalai Srinivasan pioneered radical socio-political activism grounded in principles of social justice, egalitarianism, and the denunciation of exploitation during the latter part of the nineteenth century in the Madras Presidency. Their endeavors laid the foundational framework for subsequent Dalit struggles. Nonetheless, the political milieu gradually transitioned into a dichotomy of Brahmin versus Non-Brahmin. Although the non-Brahmin movement exhibited progressive attributes, it predominantly benefited a limited faction, inadequately addressing the rights and aspirations of the Dalit populace. Consequently, the movement did not uplift the marginalized and untouchable communities, leaving a substantial swath of the demographic neglected.

The Viduthalai Chiruthaigal Katchi (VCK), colloquially referred to as the Liberation Tigers Party, has significantly influenced Dalit politics in Tamil Nadu. Established by Thol. Thirumavalavan, VCK stands as a foremost proponent of Dalit rights and representation. The party's trajectory, marked by steadfast resilience and astute strategizing, has facilitated its ascension to a prominent status since inception.[1]

The Hierarchical Caste System in India:

India's complex caste hierarchy delineates individuals into numerous social strata based on criteria such as natal origins, occupational roles, and perceived ritual purity. This stratification has persisted as a pivotal element of Indian societal fabric for millennia, tracing its antecedents to the epochs of ancient Hinduism. The caste system is classified into four predominant categories or varnas: Brahmins (priestly and scholarly class) esteemed as the apex varna, entrusted with sacerdotal duties, ceremonial rites, and the safeguarding of sacred knowledge, Kshatriyas (military and sovereign class) were linked to governance, war, and rule. , Vaishyas (commercial and agrarian class) focused on business and

agriculture, and Shudras (manual laborers and service providers) worked as servants and laborers for the other varnas. A fifth category, referred to as Dalits or 'untouchables,' exists beyond the confines of this hierarchical

framework, often subjected to systemic discrimination and violence. Insights into the primordial socioeconomic framework of ancient India can be derived from the Rig Veda,

Over time, the varna system became increasingly rigid, substantially influenced by hereditary factors. Within each varna, the concept of jati, or subcastes, emerged, further stratifying society in accordance with social hierarchy and vocational roles. These jati were often aligned with specific

professions, trades, or skills. To maintain the sanctity of social and occupational boundaries, individuals within a jati practiced endogamy, marrying solely within their own community. The caste system was largely formulated and regulated by religious and legal texts, such as the Dharmashastras and Smritis.

Dalits: Previously known as "untouchables," Dalits exist outside the four main castes. They are one of the most marginalized and oppressed groups in society, facing severe discrimination and social exclusion. Members of lower castes face significant disadvantages and systemic discrimination, while those from higher castes benefit from greater privileges and opportunities. This inequality arises from the rigid and unfair structure of the caste system, which maintains social inequity and exclusion through various political, social, and economic institutions.[2]

Characteristics of the Caste System in India

The caste in the interior of India is a singular long-standing structure that significantly influenced the identities in addition to lives possessed by countless individuals over thousands possessed by years. This complex affects aspects possessed by political, in addition to economic. We highlight features: endogamy, stratification, vocational specialization, segregation, in addition to hereditary.

Hereditary Nature

primary possessed by the distinct characteristics possessed by the caste is hereditary. Caste status is passed gravitation wards from to, meaning individuals inherit the caste possessed by. This aspect a singular impact overset for identity in addition to mobility.

Social Status: A singular person's caste plays a singular crucial role in the interior of standing. Members possessed by castes, Dalits, severe discrimination in addition to exclusion, higher castes, as brahmins, historically greater prestige in addition to privileges.

Occupation: The caste traditionally limits the types possessed by occupations available to individuals. For instance, kshatriyas typically as warriors in addition to rulers, Vaishyas engage in the interior of trade in addition to agriculture, Shudras as laborers in addition to providers, in addition to brahmins are priests in addition to scholars. Dalits, what biochemical identity don't into categories, are frequently assigned the menial jobs in addition to stigma.

in the interior of Tamil Nadu, approximately parts possessed by India, caste affects society. Castes, Dalits, faced severe discrimination in the interior of the, brahmins. In the interior of the 1900s, the non-brahmin for equality in addition to challenged brahmin. This to the Dravidian, at this temporal identity controls Tamil Nadu politics.[3]

Caste based Politics in Tamil Nadu

In the interior of Tamil Nadu, approximately in the interior of parts possessed by India, the caste is. In the interior of the castes, the Dalits, faced a singular possessed by unfair treatment, the brahmins a singular possessed by. Starting in the interior of the 1900s, the non-brahmin aimed to promote fairness in addition to brahmin. The Dravidian, greatly influenced politics in the interior of Tamil Nadu, from this earlier

Dravidian Parties:

The Justice Party, started in 1916, fought for non-Brahmin rights and Struggle for Brahminical ascendancy. The Dravidian manoeuvre was constructed on it.

DMK, founded in 1949 by C.N. Annadurai, focuses on Tamil pride, fighting caste discrimination, and helping the poor. It remains powerful in Tamil Nadu politics.

AIADMK, started by M.G. Ramachandran in 1972, also works for social justice and helps disadvantaged groups through various programs.[4]

Dalit Parties:

In the interior of Tamil Nadu, parties that overset for the rights possessed by specific communities be in possession of emerged alongside the dravidian parties.

Puthiya Tamilagam (PT), utilizing the Methodious process of k. Krishnasamy, works for the rights possessed by the devendrakula vellalar community. The talks in relation to in addition to tries to solve the economic issues this faces.[5]

Viduthalai Chiruthaigal Katchi (vck), started utilizing the Methodious process of thol. Thirumavalavan, focuses overset for the rights possessed by dalits. This possessing the characteristic of in the interior of fighting caste discrimination in addition to supporting dalit rights.

caste plays a singular role in the interior of Tamil Nadu's politics. The Dravidian parties justice, they be in possession of possessing the characteristic of criticized for not doing for dalits in addition to marginalized groups. To this, parties approximately VCK be in possession of utilize motile abilities towards antigravitation wards to overset for the specific needs in addition to rights possessed by groups. The caste in addition to politics in the interior of Tamil Nadu is complex. Not undulating the Dravidian progress in the interior of promoting justice in addition to fighting caste bias, a surplus of is needed to achieve equality in addition to representation.

Dalit Panthers and VCK

In 1972, young Dalit activists in Maharashtra started the **Dalit Panthers of India (DPI)**, taking inspiration **from America's Black Panthers**. The group spread to Tamil Nadu and other parts of India, fighting against caste discrimination and working for social justice.

The most important contributions and events that shaped the life of **A. Malaichamy**, founder of **Dalit Panthers Iyakkam (DPI)** movement in Tamil Nadu (transformed later into the Viduthalai Chiruthaigal Katchi by Thol. Thirumavalavan), titled 'Chiruthaigalin Mudhal Paichal: Maveeran

Malaichamy', was launched by Thol. Thirumavalavan on Wednesday. The book has been written by V.P. Inkulab, Madurai South District Secretary of the VCK.

One major aspect of the caste system is social segregation, where inter-caste relationships are heavily influenced by strict societal norms. There are clear boundaries between castes, enforced through numerous social, economic, and cultural practices. For example, traditional Indian society often sees different castes living in separate villages or neighborhoods. Lower castes, especially Dalits, are usually pushed to less desirable areas on the outskirts, while higher castes occupy central, more sought-after locations.[6]

Viduthalai Chiruthaigal Katchi (VCK):**Formation and Ideological Foundation**

Thol.Thirumavalavan started the Viduthalai Chiruthaigal Katchi (VCK) in Tamil Nadu in 1982.This party comes from the Dalit Panthers and seeks equality and justice. VCK fights against caste discrimination and supports Dalit rights. It is inspired by Ambedkarism, which promotes justice,

equality, and ending caste differences. The party aims to close the economic gap between Dalits and other groups. The Dalit community connects with VCK's dedication to Ambedkarism. In politics, Dalit leaders struggle because larger Dravidian parties dominate. This makes it hard for them to address Dalit issues and affect policies. Dalits face economic challenges, as there are big gaps in wealth compared to other groups. Also, divisions based on sub-castes and regions weaken the Dalit community's fight for rights.

Leadership and Organizational Structure:

The growth of VCK and its importance in Tamil Nadu politics is mainly due to Thol.Thirumavalavan's strong leadership. He connects well with the Dalit community and understands their problems. Because of him, VCK has a clear direction and a strong voice in politics. The party's local network helps support Dalit rights and get people to vote. VCK's success in elections and its political power come from its ability to bring the Dalit community together.

Electoral Performance:

VCK has participated in many elections in Tamil Nadu, both alone and with major parties like the DMK. Having seats in the parliament and legislative assembly has been important for the party's election success.[7]

Lok Sabha Elections

Year	Seats Won	Percentage of Votes	Remarks
1999	0 / 2	-	As Tamil Maanila Congress candidates
2004	0 / 8	-	As Janata Dal (United) candidates
2009	1 / 20	0.18%	-
2014	0 / 20	0.11%	-
2019	2 / 20	0.8%	Ravikumar (writer) contested in Dravida Munnetra Kazhagam symbol
2024	2 / 22	2.25%	Achieved recognized Party

Tamil Nadu Legislative Assembly elections

Election Year	Election	Votes Polled	Won	Change of Seats	Alliance	Result
2006	13th Assembly	426,321	2 / 9	Increase 2	ADMK +	Won
2011	14th Assembly	555,965	0 / 10	Decrease 2	DMK +	Lost
2016	15th Assembly	331,849	0 / 25	No Change	DMDK+	Lost
2021	16th Assembly	457,763	4 / 6	Increase 4	DMK +	Won

Problems of Dalit Assertion in Tamil Nadu:

Dalits in Tamil Nadu face many challenges, even with help from groups like VCK. Discrimination and Social Stigma Dalits still deal with unfair treatment and social shame, making it hard for them to fight for their rights and improve their lives. Marginalization in Politics Larger Dravidian parties often keep Dalit leaders and groups from gaining real political power. This makes it harder for them to push for issues important to Dalits and influence laws. Economic Inequalities Dalits find it hard to achieve equal

social and economic status because there are still money gaps between them and other groups. Internal Divisions Different sub-castes and local groups within the Dalit community can weaken their ability to stand together for their rights.

Conclusion:

The complex interrelation of social justice and the caste movement has left a deep impression on the political landscape of Tamil Nadu. Traditionally, hegemony against the non-Brahmin politics has shackled the Dalit representation in spite of the efforts put forth by early pioneers. Powerful Dalit leaders have argued that a different personality other than other political identities will help remove this inequality. VCK has emerged as one of the important political parties in Tamil Nadu. Unlike other Dalit organizations, VCK operates at every level on social justice, secularism, and anti-caste politics. Its strategic alliances, especially with the DMK, and its sharp opposition to Hindutva have increased its political power. Under the leadership of Thol. Thirumavalavan. This ability to garner support from a different section of society helped Thirumavalavan stand apart from other Dalit parties, which were more specific in their approach. Nonetheless, VCK lags in political clout and independence. Overall, this multi-pronged strategy made VCK stand out as a unique and indispensable player in Tamil Nadu's politics.

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INDIAN FEDERALISM AND REGIONAL DEMANDS**Dr. Umesha**

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Abstract

Federal and unitary government divided on the basis of concentration and distribution of powers among central and regional governments. In federal government powers of the state divided between national and regional governments, both are independent and autonomous in their respective sphere of powers. In this paper an attempt has been made to explain federal features of Indian constitution. It explains various forms of regional demands in India. It explains impact of regionalism on Indian polity. It also briefly explains remedies for eradication of regionalism.

Keywords: *Federalism, regionalism unitary system. Decentralisation, regional government, powers, government, Constitution.*

Introduction:

Modern governments are divided as unitary and federal government. In unitary government all powers of state vested in single central government and for administrative convenience powers are divided on the basis of territorial to the regional or provincial governments. In this system provincial government have no independent or autonomous powers, they cannot act independently and have no decision powers in vital matters, and they are only implementing agencies which are decision taken by the central government. The powers of the provincial governments granted by the central government not by the constitution. Central government increase or decrease powers of provincial government or abolish the provincial governments at any time. Some nations adopted unitary system of government for example England, China, Italy, France, Belgium, Japan, Norway, Sweden, Spain etc. In other hand in federal government powers of the state divided between central/national and provincial government by the constitution both are independent autonomous in their respective sphere of powers. Provincial government has powers to take decisions in their respective powers. In this system powers are divided on the basis of functionally. Dual polity, division of powers written constitution common features of federal polity. Both government are independent autonomous in their respective sphere of powers. U S, Canada, Australia, Switzerland and Brazil etc adopted federal system of government.

Indian constitution established federal government. In India dual government those are central and provincial government existed and both are derives their powers from constitution, both are independent in their respective powers. But the Indian federalism quite different from USA. Federalism it comes into disintegration form. The framers of constitution inserted both unitary and federal features and make strong central government due to the various reason during that time like Maintenance of unity and integrity of the nation, to prevent fissiparous tendency to tackle the problems and challenge of partition of country, threat of war or attack by neighbor country China and Pakistan, problems faced by nation during that time like illiteracy, poverty, unemployment, underdevelopment and lack of development in various sectors etc. these are effectively handled by only strong central government.

Features of Indian Federalism :

- **Dual polity:** Indian constitution establishes dual government central and state government. Central government deals with national importance like foreign policy, defense, finance etc. State government deals with local matters like health, sanitation, education, agriculture, local government etc.
- **Written Constitution:** Constitution not only written but lengthiest document. It specifies organization structure of both central and state government.
- **Division of powers:** Constitution divides both governments powers in three lists, union list, state list and concurrent list, residuary power lies with central government.
- **Rigid constitution:** The provision regarding federal like centre-state relations, some provision of judiciary should amend only followed by rigid procedures.
- **Independent Judiciary:** The Constitution establish independent judiciary, it is guardian of constitution. Center – state disputes can settled by supreme court.
- **Supremacy of Constitution:** The Constitution is the supreme law of the land . The laws enacted by centre and the states must confirm to its provisions. In case they violated the constitutional provisions they can be declared invalid by supreme court or high courts through their power of judicial review. Thus organs of the both government legislative, executive and judiciary must operate within the jurisdiction prescribed by constitution.
- **Bicameral Legislature:** Parliament consist two houses upper house called as Rajya Sabha and lower house called as Lok sabha. Rajya sabha represent state interest while Lok sabha represent the people of India.

Regional Demands:

The regionalism is common factor in Indian federal structure. It has antithetical to nationalism and hindrance to national unity and integrity. The term regionalism associates with region, region means geographical location, or more or less extensive part of the earth surface. Regionalism means sentiment towards a particular region, it means part of nation state marked by homogeneity of culture, language and community of economic and other factors. It is love for one's area of living or particular region to which one belongs. Regionalism is tendency which makes the people feel that their interest in linguistic, political, economic and cultural are distinct and separate from similar interest of the people outside the region. Regionalism inculcate in people of particular region to organise themselves into a distinct political unit for the protection and promotion of their specific interests.

Factors for rise Regionalism in India:

There are many factors responsible for growth regionalism in India.

➤ Regional diversity :

India is land of diversity many regions of people have their distinct language, culture, and historical traditions these are very sensitive. The linguistic factor gave rise to linguistic regionalism.

➤ Tribal Factors :

Some regions of India especially north-eastern states inhabited by many tribes. These tribes have their own traditions, culture and language. They have highly proud of their culture and traditions and stood apart from mainstream of national life and history. It is naturally they fear about conserve their culture and traditions. It leads to merge to the mainstream of national life .

➤ **Religious factors:**

Religious factor responsible to rise of regionalism and birth to the movement for the division of pre-independence India into two nations India and Pakistan. At present some rebel Sikhs demand for their home land Khalistan.

➤ **Economic Factors:**

Economic factors is vital in rise of regionalism. In India some regions developed and some regions are under developed and economically uneven. For instance Telangana in Andhra Pradesh, Vidarba in Maharashtra, Kalyan Karnataka (Hydrabad Karnataka) region in Karnataka should be traced to the uneven economic development of the respective regions. Some regions within the state also uneven development this leads to conflict between developed and under developed regions on question of location of projects distribution of waters etc. In 1950 the extreme form of regionalism arose in Chennai, but in matter of regional development. Chennai was a developed state.

➤ **Linguistic Regionalism:**

Language have remained formidable basis of regionalism. The policy of linguistic reorganisation of state has been main responsible for growth of regionalism for instance Kodava demand for autonomous region of Coorg region in Karnataka state.

➤ **Democratic Federal Constitutionalism:**

In Indian federalism the ruling political parties are opposite centre has unnecessary interference in state government. Misuse of Article 356 of the constitution, dissolution of state legislature, discriminatory attitude in the allocation grants to the state.

➤ **Ethnic Factor :**

Ethnic factors also leads to regionalism. For example in 1960 Dravidan movement in Tamil Nadu was rise demand for Dravida nationalism. This claim is based on wide spread evidence of the genetic difference between north and south Indians.

➤ **Regional Political Parties:**

In Indian Political system existence of multi-party system. some regional political parties criticise the intervention of central government in state matters and demand for more autonomous ex DMK and AIDMK in Tamil Nadu, TDP in Andhra Pradesh, TMC in West Bengal, BJD in Orissa etc.

➤ **Differentiate Tendency of Central Government:**

The central government while grant in aid to the states it make differentiate then states have dissatisfied towards the central government and claim for autonomous and leads to separate list movement.

➤ **Regional Imbalance :**

In India all regions uneven by geographical naturally and infrastructure facilities, North Indian states compare to south Indian states and Northern east states naturally enrich by fertile agriculture land, river water resources and located heavy industrial sectors. this factor also leads to regionalism.

Forms of Regionalism:

➤ **Demands for secession :**

Khalistan demand by some rebel Sikhs, Dravidnadu demand by Tamilians, Jammu and Kashmir, North- East States demand for Separate Statehood

In beginning of the independent India number of states was 16. After Reorganisation commission of 1956 increase demand for Separate Statehood. In 1989 number of states increase

to 25 in 2000 it was increased to 28. In 2014 June 2nd formation Telangana state by Dividing united Andhra Pradesh .

➤ **Demand for Full statehood:**

In Indian federal system have not only states but also it includes some union territories. Union territories completely administration by central government. These union territories demand for full statehood . in 1971 Himachal Pradesh getting full statehood. Later Manipur, Tripura Mizoram , Arunachal Pradesh and Sikkim have got full statehood. Recently New Delhi demand for full statehood. Arvind Kejriwal former Chief Minister of New Delhi often claimed 1 for full statehood to New Delhi.

➤ **Demand for autonomous :**

In Indian Political system after fourth general election (1967) some regional political parties come to power in state. DMK in Tamil Nadu , TDP in Andhra Pradesh , TMC in West Bengal and Akali dal in Punjab etc. these regional parties oppose the hegemony of Congress party and unnecessary intervention in state politics and demand for more autonomous for states.

In June 2000 Jammu – Kashmir legislative assembly passed a resolution and sent to the central government for more autonomous for state. Central government rejected this resolution out rightly.

Demand for regional autonomy within a State:

➤ In Indian union some particular communities or sections of particular region strive for conserve their uniqueness for this purpose they demand for particular region, this tendency leads to regionalism. Ladakhis in Jammu – Kashmir , Gorkha land demand in west Bengal, Bodoland in Assam, Kodavasa in Karnataka. Etc.

➤ **Inter -state disputes :**

There are disputes boundary disputes for example between Karnataka and Maharashtra on Belgaum where Marathi speaking population is surrounded by Kannada speaking people, between Kerala and Karnataka on Kasargod. important dispute regarding the use of water source was over the use of water resources of three rivers mainly Narmada, Krishna and Cauvery in which states of Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Gujarat and Maharashtra were involved. Disputes also arose between use of Cauvery waters among the states of Tamil Nadu, Kerala and Karnataka. the dispute over river Mahadayi between Karnataka and Goa. Another dispute arose among the states of Maharashtra, Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh over the use and distribution of waters of the Krishna River. Disputes between Punjab, Rajasthan and Himachal Pradesh over the use of waters of Ravi River.

➤ **Sons of Soil Policy :**

This is regarding to the employment should given to the native state peoples. Karnataka for Kannadigas. Tamilnadu for Tamils Maharashtra for Marathis . Recently some states adopted the policy for employment for local leads to strengthen the regionalism. In some state there is movement against to expel from state outsiders who are come from other states. Some Northern states like Assam Manipur Mizoram struggle for expel for foreigners.

➤ **Militant Regionalism :**

This type of regionalism arise from formations some organisations or senas for protect interest of original inhabitants from outsiders who come from different for employment trade, business and other occupations. Shiva Sena in Maharashtra, Karnataka Rakashna Vedithe in Karnataka, Jaganatha Sene in Orissa , Tamil Sene in Tamilnadu Sardar Sene in Gujrat etc. These are claimed for employment and government services for original inhabitants, for fulfillment this

objectives they followed violent and intimidation activities. This tendency begins in 1960 in Assam against the Bengali peoples, later it spread in other states. In Maharashtra Shiva Sena engaged in this activities against the south Indian people. This in turn start as revenge form in other states.

➤ **Linguistic Regionalism:**

In Indian union Linguistic regionalism is one form of regionalism . Creation of states on the basis language on recommentatin of state reorganisation commission leads different language speaking people demand for separate states,

Impact of Regionalism:

- Regionalism is major hurdle to nationalism and one of the major challenges to smooth working for Indian democracy. It develops parochial and narrow attitude as against the unity and integration of the nation. It has left manifold impact on the Indian polity.
- It has given rise to demand for separate states. The areas which were neglected have demand separate states in the hope that this would ensure quicker development of the area.
- It has created feeling of regionalism and contributed to tension.
- Regional Imbalance have contributed to tension between rural and urban areas resulting the urbanisation and migration.
- The growing social tension in the society is also largely due to existing imbalance between various regions. On account of these imbalance between various categories of workers try to migrate to areas where big industries are located
- It is cause to development of violent attitude because the backward region people begins movement, agitation and demonstration for brining development in case government not fulfill their demands they engaged in violent activities.
- It is cause to rise of sub- regionalism within the states due to uneven development of various regions. Under developed region peoples started struggle for development and gradually they developed sub -regionalism which is also obstacle to smooth working of state government.

Suggestion for Eradicating Regionalism:

Regionalism in India has been natural in our federal polity, but no can appreciate and justify the aggressive, anti national and parochial regionalism. The growing intensity of terrorism and militancy as means of pursuing narrowly conceived regional goal is indeed alarming. It has checked and controlled immediately. Militant regionalism in particular requires immediate and effective handling.

- Secession in every form needs to be checked by forceful implementation of the law and well designed Socialisation process
- End of policy of appeasement
- Doing away with regional imbalance
- Disciplined role by regional and national political parties
- Top priority to the economic development of deprived zones
- Developed means of transport and communication
- Proper education
- Development of self imposed code of conduct of by mass media
- Create enough employment opportunity
- Provide Special Packages to backward states
- Special category status to Bifurcated State in India
- Improve National Integration
- Protection of the interest of tribes and development of trible belts.

- Erosion of Democratic institutions
- Prevention of regionalisation of Indian History
- Centre should never try to act as a big brother over a states
- Security of socio-economic justice to the Indian hilly tribes
- Cooperative Federalism .

Formation of the **NITI Aayog has been a positive step to enhance cooperative federalism** by fostering the involvement of the State Governments of India in the economic policy-making process using a bottom-up approach.

Conclusion:

Indian federalism is one of the unique federalism in the world. Framers of the constitution adopted federal and unitary features in the constitution. It worked as federal in normal time and unitary in emergency and unforeseen situation. The regionalism has one of the major issue and challenge to working of Indian federalism. It has inevitable in federal system, Indian regional diversity, uneven development, Pluralist society, attitude of central government towards state government main reasons for rise of regionalism, but these regionalism turn into impediment to federal system when it has manifestation in violent and militant form. Central government play's effective role in eradication of regionalism. When different political parties rule both central and state government the demand for regionalism expressed in ardent form, and hurdle to smooth relations of both government. Both national and regional political parties to resort method of cooperation and coordination for solving problems and issue arise from regionalism.

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GLOBALIZATION AND POLITICS - AN OVERVIEW ON ITS PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS IN INDIA

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Abstract

Globalization is the concept of connectivity. Generally it is the bridge between nations, cultures, companies and people. Today we are living in “Global Village” and it impact on all the dimensions of society and the nation. According to World Bank – “Globalization is the only one power in the world which connected economies and societies together”. Globalisation plays a vital role on Nations especially like India with 5th largest emerging nation in the world. In politics it impact on state and its governance are unavoidable.

Key words: Globalisation, Politics, Nation, Society and Development.

INTRODUCTION:

Globalization is the concept of integration and exchange of economic, social and cultural aspects of people beyond national boundaries. According to Kevin O Rourke and Jeffrey Williamson (Economists of Ireland & America) – 19th century itself when the sudden drop in transport cost the prices of commodities in Europe and Asia to converge. After 20th century it popularise and got expansion in 21st century.

Present Scenario of All Humans without borders:

Human Being - Political Being - Global Being

1 INDIA AND GLOBALIZATION :

In the year 1991 India implemented Liberalization Privatisation and Globalization policy to open world market and improve economic situation and to achieve development in various sectors.

LPG policy allowed 05 major Initiatives. They are ;

1. Abolition of old and unchanged license Raj system with open and free procedures.
2. Allow private sector to invest and establish business.
3. Attraction towards FDI – Foreign Direct Investments.
4. Tax benefits or Tax holidays.
5. Minimizing Import duties and taxes.

Results of LPG Policy ;

1. Free flow for FDI and raised investment ratio in India
2. Employment opportunities increased.
3. GDP and Per capita income increased.
4. Reduction in Imports and increase in exports.

PROBLEMS OF GLOBALIZATION :**1. Economic Problems:****A. *Richer become more richer ;***

In India the gap between rich and poor was increased drastically and rich getting advantages and opportunities in covid -19 situation also. But life of poor people got worsens and they are not able to lead a good and qualitative life.

B. *Myth of free trade ;*

Globalisation declares itself supports free trade but free trade is under control of developed nations. They have a control on trade through WTO and other international organisations like IMF and World Bank. Poor and developing nations like India having a trade according to the need of developed nations.

C. *Fake and duplication of products ;*

Due to free trade and opportunities various fake and duplication of products have entered to the world market and created confusions and havocs among the customer by offering cheap price and other offers. In India there is huge market for fake and duplicate products from China and other countries with similar name, design, colours and usage of the products.

2

2. Political Problems:**A. *Neo Colonialism ;***

Various political analysts stated that the globalisation is nothing new concept and it is the new version of Neo Colonialism and Imperialism. Country like India with around 300 years of colonial state under British Raj aware that globalization is inevitable and uncontrollable.

B. *Threat to national sovereignty ;*

Through MNC's and TNC's developed nations kept poor and developing nations under its control and interfere in their policy formulations. Ex: countries like USA, Russia and England try to pressurise India to favour themselves.

C. *Pressure and lobby on government ;*

In policies, programmes and plans non state actors' pressure and lobby on government to favour themselves and make advantages for trade and business, tax benefits, loan weaving and other benefits.

D. *Misuse of tax exemptions/tax holiday ;*

Various companies misusing government's provisions of tax exemptions and showing periodical losses and hiding the profit and loss ratio. This attitude of companies resulted in flow of wealth of India to other countries.

3. Social Problems:**A. *Insecurity in employment ;***

Employment is not guaranteed to the employees where the employment status is fully based on market conditions. Hence there is no job security. Employees of private sector need to be ready every time about their employment condition.

B. *Transfer of jobs ;*

Jobs are continuously under modification on demand and needy basis. Its need to upgradation and change of job profiles. Ex: Office assistant is also typist and computer operator. Before there are existence of 03 jobs - Office assistant, Typist and Computer Operator.

3

D. Exploitation on labours ;

In India there is an established labour law for welfare and security of employees. Due to globalisation unwanted competition, market demands the workers exploited by the companies.

These are the major challenges of globalization.

SOLUTIONS FOR GLOBALISATION :

1. **More Competition ;** Globalization expands the opportunities and maximizes competition in market and allows all stake holders competes each other for betterment of customers. Due to competition in India, there are chances of choices of products with good quality and attractive prices.
2. **Efficiency in Productivity ;** Due to use of technology and advancement with skilled workers the productivity will increase effectively. In India private sector with the help of globalization's sake high technology and skilled workers achieved highest productivity with high production in every year and also providing periodical training programs on skills, upgradation, programming and other essentials.
3. **Free flow for Investment ;** Before globalization developing nation like India faced lack of investment resources for development activities. After 1991 with implementation of LPG policy India opened for Foreign Direct Investment and gathered huge investment for infrastructure and developmental activities.
4. **Increase in Transport and Communication ;** Innovation and technology made transport and communication easier, cheaper and accessible to public. Hence there is an increase of facilities, modes and varieties of transport and communication.

Concluding Remarks :

Today globalization moving faster with indefinite speed but there are no solutions from super power nations for negative side of globalization. The problems like Borderless international terrorism, Global warming and organized crimes are uneaten fruits of globalization. Countries like India opened for globalization but not having a capacity of curb and control over it. With strong political will and organized efforts, we can solve the problems and challenges of Globalization effectively. 4

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YOUTH PARTICIPATION IN POLITICS

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Abstract

In my paper, mainly I concentrated about the role of youth in political participation and how the democracy influences to the youth in optimistic way to cultivate and how the youth will improve the democratic arrangement in present consequence. Since the youth are the real heroes to bring the productive system. Youths are the real supremacy in the changing system specifically in India. Each and every youth have to dynamically contribute in the Democratic Nation action and give their unconditional service sloping contributions in various fields. And after the election process also youth people have to definitely continue their role to impede in state if their functions out of their jurisdiction and unseeded up their decision and youths have to stake their opinion against Government decision. Whether it is State or Central Government decision should be taken biased that civic rights responsibility have to take care by the youths through their political cultural.

Youths have absolution their powers with their commitment and they have to try to bring realistic changes in the society as a wellbeing Society. Each youth have raise the question if it is essential when Government UN favour of people. Youth Political participation is taking place within a setting of democratic interchange, including a world-wide failure in the State of Democracy, decrease space for civil society, separation of the political and social space, monetary emergency and intelligence, speedy digitalisation, etc. impact of the Covid-19 pandemic and most recently war. In this background, we are beholding a lack of opinion in political establishments, a collective disengagement from the political scheme and a debility in youth participation in formal politics.

Keyword: Civic Rights, Responsibilities, Political culture, Political participation, Power of Youth

YOUTH POLITICAL PARTICIPATION

INTRODUCTION

Youths want to bring amendment in present politics, but they feel voices are guaranteed to get lost in the political declamation. The field of politics in India is routinely supposed as something that is not suitable to the educated crowds. The young people participation has been majorly casual and even though the youth continue to contribute in local elections there is a need for a more dynamic and formal participation in politics to (www.ijcrt.org © 2021 IJCRT | Volume 9, Issue 10 October 2021 | ISSN: 2320-2882) emerge the changes which is obligatory for the country's improvement. Politics has become as a last career appeal among the teenagers, due to uncontrolled corruption, favouritism, caste politics, and lack of accountability and lack of openness. This paper explore

As a result, most of our potential human resources choose to go abroad for relaxing their perpetually as soon as they complete their education politics need to open and should encourage the younger generation into conventional politics. Young leaders personalise energy and interest and can be infinitely effectual in forming policies for themselves regarding contemporary issues and difficulties. Young generation should be the pillar of our future India, more ideas to be produced and they should be stimulate the younger responsible for choosing which cultural beliefs are going to work for the welfares of humankind. Participation of young people will also make certain a larger sense of inclusiveness in the democratic scheme. (www.ijcrt.org © 2021 IJCRT | Volume 9, Issue 10 October 2021 | ISSN: 2320-2882 IJCRT2110084 International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT) www.ijcrt.org a698) The country like India greatly needs some young leaders and, we feel that the system needs to be changed but, we don't want to take the responsibility on our shoulders. In our country the main posts are mostly occupied by the political representatives above 50 years of age this should be get altered.

Political Participation of youth needs to be prolonged beyond the casting of a vote through reservation for youth in political parties as well as in the Parliament. The right balance of young capacity and young politicians can lead to change in insights of politics and can build public faith in political system. (Martikainenetal., 2005)

YOUTHS CHALLENGES IN POLITICAL PARTICIPATION

The role of Youth is an active section of society whose members are essential for the growth of the Nation. The values, ideals, morals, Ethics, that each of these members has instructed therefore matters and has a bearing upon society because the younger group are the creators of a new world that has their ambitions. Without the youth is a resource for the economy and also is the sign of a society's expectations. Identifying the dynamic role that is played by the youth, the government has passed a resolution that reads, "Youth for Community- Community for Youth", which highlights the role of the youth in the advancement of society.

Politics is participation of all residents of the State therefore political parties of the State act as an organiser to reach each individual in the activities of politics. Political parties are recognized as one among the pillars of Democracy. They unite the different opinions of each individuals in to one feature of the State. A political parties is predictable to meet the potentials of the people from one generation to generation. The role of Youths in politics is critically observed in Contemporary retro. The role of civil society is the major instrument to modification or to recreate the political system when the system is not in the proper way. Hence the active assemblies of civil society have strength and status to help the civil culture group in to the right track of political direction. But, youths have facing many encounters in existing politics to resolve political exploitations and to support of youth politics.

Contemporary democracies are faithfully linked to the opinion of representation. Many tutors use "democracy" and "representation" interchangeably, although not all forms of representation are democratic. However, the two terms are closely related, as representation has become the major form of establishing modern democracies. The main principle of exemplification has continued unmovable over the spans: People's representatives should reproduce the will of the people and act consequently in demonstrative political forms. In recent years, modern characteristic democracy has faced plentiful experiments and disapprovals, many of which relate to the excellence of democracy in general and the superiority of representation in specific. Various public opinion inspections have exposed an upward adverse emotion toward the main institutions of representative democracy. Belief in these establishments, as well as gratification with the functioning of democracy in universal, is exceptionally low, accomplishment critical levels in some countries. The significance of youth participation in Indian politics cannot be overstated. Not only do young people represent the future of the nation, but they also bring fresh perspectives innovative ideas, and a palpable sense of urgency to address pressing socio-political issues. From advocating for environmental sustainability to championing social justice causes, youth-led movements have captured the imagination of the public and catalysed discourse on critical issues affecting the country. This paper aims to explore the historical context, current trends, challenges, and opportunities surrounding youth engagement in Indian politics. By analysing the influence of youth on policy agendas, electoral dynamics, and societal transformation, it seeks to provide insights into the evolving role of young people as agents of change within the democratic fabric of India. Furthermore, the research will highlight the potential pathways for empowering and nurturing youth leadership, fostering a culture of political engagement, and realizing the aspirations of a progressive and inclusive society.

In examining the role of youth in Indian politics, this research paper contributes to a deeper understanding of the dynamics shaping the nation's democratic landscape and underscores the imperative of harnessing the energy and potential of youth for the advancement of democratic ideals and societal progress. The significance of youth participation in Indian politics cannot be overstated. Not only do young people represent the future of the nation, but they also bring fresh perspectives, innovative ideas, and a palpable sense of urgency to address pressing socio-political issues. From advocating for environmental sustainability to championing social justice causes affecting the country. This paper aims to explore the historical context, current trends, and challenges surrounding youth engagement in Indian politics. By analysing the influence of youth on policy agendas, electoral dynamics, and societal transformation, it seeks to provide insights into the evolving role of young people as agents of change within the democratic fabric of India. Some youth are putting that belief into action through various forms of civic and political engagement, and many more say they might do so if given the opportunity. But too many young people—often those from historically marginalized groups—continue to say they don't feel well-informed or qualified enough to participate in political life. That points to ongoing challenges in ensuring the equitable civic preparation and participation of all young people. Youth are making a difference as activists, as leaders in community development and political aspiration, and by their record level of volunteerism. In many parts of the world, they may be perceived as apathetic or disengaged, but this is largely inaccurate. Worldwide, youth are bypassing traditional forms of political participation (e.g. voting) through their activism and volunteering (Youth and Millennium Development 2005:6).

Major discoveries from our youth survey include:

- When asked why they feel the way they do about the direction of the country, many young people who say the country is on the wrong track cite inadequate action on issues they care about like inflation and cost of living, crime, and inequality. Some youth who are pleased with the country's direction cited progress on some of those issues or the results of the 2022 election as reasons for their optimism. Crucially, while some young people who stated they weren't sure how they would characterize the direction of the country said they weren't following politics, others said they had mixed feelings because they saw both good and bad things happening in the country.
- Many youth are also concerned about the country's values and distrustful of major institutions. Nearly two-thirds of young people (62%) expressed concern about the values of the American people, and 45% said they believe that the country is failing to live up to its promises of freedom and fairness, compared to just 18% who believe the country has lived up to these promises.
- Less than a third of young people said they trust either of the two major political parties, their state government, Congress, or the President. Among political institutions, the GOP and Congress garnered the highest levels of distrust from youth: 49% and 41%, respectively.
- 55% of young people (ages 18-29) say the country is going in the wrong direction and only 16% believe it's on the right track.
- 76% of respondents believe young people have the power to change the country, and 77% believe there are ways for them to get involved.
- A third of youth (32%) have signed a petition or joined a boycott, and 1 in 7 youth have participated in a march or demonstration, with even more youth (28%) saying they plan to protest or would do so or would if presented with the opportunity.

- Half of youth say they're "as well-informed as most people" and only 40% say they feel well-qualified to participate in politics.
- The majority of young people (55%) believe the country is heading in the wrong direction, with 16% saying it's on the right track and the rest (28%) saying they're not sure. There are some differences among groups of youth: for example, youth of color are more likely than white youth to say the country is on the right track or that they are unsure. Some of that may be partially explained by young people's partisan preferences, since youth of color are more likely to support Democrats and their view of the current presidential administration may shape their view of the country's direction. Young people who reported that they didn't vote in 2022 were more likely to say they weren't sure how they felt about the way things are going in the United States.
- Young people's hope for the future may also be a reflection of their belief that their generation can and should engage in civic life and effect change. At the same time, there appears to be a gap between young people's interest in political participation and whether they feel prepared and qualified to do so.
- Young people have a strong sense of both individual and collective efficacy: 74% said that there are things they can do to make the world a better place, and 76% believe that their age group has the power to change things. Even more (83%) recognize the potential of young people working with other generations to create change.
- In addition, almost two-thirds of young people (62%) say that their political views are a somewhat or very important part of their personal identity. Young women of color, LGBTQ youth, youth with college experience, and the older segment of the cohort (ages 25-29) are all more likely to say that politics are an important part of their identity, indicating both how marginalized identities and educational and lived experience can contribute to the formation of such political identities.
- However, while a majority of youth have a strong sense that they could achieve change and a strong personal political identity, many don't feel informed or qualified enough to participate in politics. Only half of youth say they feel they're "as well-informed as most people," which underscores our previous finding that 1 in 5 youth who did not vote in 2022 said they about the candidates or the voting process.
- Even fewer youth in our survey (40%) say that they feel well-qualified to participate in politics, and youth from groups that have historically held less political power were even less likely to feel qualified. For example, 34% of youth of color say they feel qualified to participate in politics, compared to 44% of white youth. Young people ages 22-29 were also more likely to feel qualified than youth ages 18-21, who are often neglected by parties, campaigns, and organizations.

The relevance of youth to the total political and developmental process of societal transformation cannot be over emphasized. The Department of Political Science and Social Affairs of the United Nations, while examining challenges and contributions of the youth towards the realization of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), observed that: Youth are making a difference as activist, as leaders in community development and political aspiration, and by their record level of volunteerism. In many parts of the world, they may be perceived as apathetic or disengaged, but this is largely inaccurate. Worldwide, youth are by- passing traditional form of political participation (e.g. voting) through their activism and volunteering (Youth and Millennium Development 2005: Apart from the issue of

numerical strength, global trend is toward emphasizing the primacy of youth in the developmental process, with deliberate efforts by national governments to create conditions that will encourage youth to utilize their energies and resourcefulness for growth and sustainable development of their nations.

However, the prevailing conditions in much of the developing nations, especially Nigeria, have seriously extenuated the potentials of the youth as agents of social change. These challenges range from the economic and social to the cultural. The treacherous triangle of poverty, illiteracy and unemployment in which the bulk of Nigerian youths are currently trapped, has severely challenged their sensibility and has in the long run given rise to what sociologists term attitudes of fatalism, resignation and acceptance of the situation (Haralambos, 2001). The persistence of these social problems has created an environment where youth are cheaply available for manipulation by self-seeking politicians. Poverty, illiteracy and unemployment are interrelated conditions that generate human needs and therefore constitute a state of deprivation.

As the youth continue to remain in this state, there is pent-up emotions and untapped energies. They provide cheap labour to execute the design of political gladiators and ethnic champions. In an apparent indictment of Nigerian politicians, Togbolo observed: "They take advantage of the poverty-stricken nature of the country to exploit the people, politicians are fond (sic) of using the youth restive nature as a political strategy to have their way" (Togbolo, 2006:8) In developing a theoretical base for this paper, Almond's structural functionalism provides an appropriate framework of analysis. In his search for a functional theory of the polity, Almond proceeds from the point of view that every society is a system with inter-related parts. A system is defined as an entity made up of interconnected and interrelated parts. Organized human society fits into this connotation of system, herein referred to as the social system (Varma, 2003).

The basic assumption of the theory is that, for a social system to survive and maintain its going concern, a certain degree of order and stability is required. To achieve this order and stability, the theory maintained that every functional parts of the social system must perform its role. It is this functional pre-requisite that serves to connect the various parts and thus integrate the social system as an organic system. Thus, from a functionalist point of view: The social system has certain basic needs which must be met if it is to survive. These needs are known as functional pre-requisites. The function of any part of the society is its contribution to the maintenance of the society (Haralambos, 2001:11) We can treat or analyze the youth from this theoretical perspective as an important segment of the social system with specific functions to perform.

YOUTH EMPOWERMENT IN POLITICAL PARTICIPATION

"Everything was better in Soeharto's reign. Yes they're corrupt, but at least prices were stable and we were safe," one of them said. He was not joking when he told that to me and my friends. I believe that more people believe in the political reform and democracy now. However, we should not overlook a pivotal point that every transition into democracy has to pass. The statement from the walking vendor shows that Indonesia has not yet safe, even though we have done relatively better than other emerging democracies.¹ This essay is an attempt to answer the abovementioned challenge. It will elaborate these following points: 1. The ability of democracy to deliver its promises (fulfilling the expectations of the people, from security to welfare and justice) will define its fate. Democracy arrived with a lot of promises (including security, political rights, equality before the law, welfare, justice, effective and clean government, etc.).

When people perceive democracy is not delivering its promises, the danger of a democratic reversal is eminent. By the way, a reversal did really happen in 1959, when the 1 Larry Diamond, "Indonesia's

Place in Global Democracy”, in Edward Aspinall and Marcus Mietzner (eds.), *Problems of Democratisation in Indonesia: Elections, Institutions and Society* (Singapore: ISEAS, 2010) democratic Constitutional Assembly was dissolved because of a political deadlock and the popular President was calling to “bury the parties”.² 2. However, democracy is not an automatic machine to fulfill all expectations. Whether democracy can deliver or not depends on how the game named democracy is played by the people. It won’t work when most people are becoming bystanders and leave it to politicians nurtured by authoritarian regime in the past. Participation is one of the most important keys. 3. If participation is the key, how to boost the precious public participation? In this context, youth is the key. In 2005, young people (15-34 years old) made up around one third of the total populations (\pm 77 million people).³ They are also a vibrant, dynamic, and creative part of the society and well-connected to technology’s state-of-the art (from Twitter to BlackBerry). 4. To empower the youth for making democracy work, we should know the right way to activate them. Indonesia’s Democracy: Overpromise, Underdeliver? “In the past, corruption was done under the table. Now, even the table is taken away” -Political joke, written in a sticker put in a public bus Before we go further, I would like to highlight one important notion: “the progress paradox”.⁴ Dissatisfaction to democracy’s performance is not always about ‘objective truth’, but sometimes more defined by perception. Even political scientists do not have identical perception on the performance of Indonesia’s democracy. Which one is Indonesia: democratic success story or a flawed democracy? According to Marcus Mietzner and Edward Aspinall, there are three broad schools of thought: (1) Democratic change has been superficial, with core structures of power remaining unchanged (Robison and Hadiz, 2004; Boudreau, 2009); (2) Indonesia has done exceptionally well in consolidating democracy, especially from comparative viewpoint (MacIntyre and Ramage, 2008; Freedom House, 2009); (3) Middle ground: some democratic progress but still crippled by severe structural problems –e.g. corruption and weak law enforcement (Davidson, 2009).

Youth empowerment and Democratic Governance Thematic Trust Fund (DGTTF) issued a call for proposals from UNDP Country Offices in support of innovative and catalytic projects on youth to inform public policy-making, training youth as effective leaders, extending access to justice, opening space for youth empowerment and democratic governance. There were a total of proposals that were approved, with being from Latin America and the Caribbean, coming from the Arab States, coming from Asia and the Pacific, coming from Central and Eastern Europe/Commonwealth of Independent States, and coming. In a number of the nations where the study was carried out, the exclusion of young people was quite clear, and this exclusion often intersected with other types of marginalization related to gender, geography, culture, or community. Activities that are included throughout all of the initiatives include bolstering young advocacy organizations, offering high-quality research to facilitate interaction with public authorities, and encouraging the formation of national youth councils and plans. A number of initiatives focus a significant emphasis on the use of information technology and social media. There are many other types of innovative solutions, such as IJAER/ July-August 2022/Volume-11/Issue-4 ISSN: 2278-9677 Copyright@ijaer.org Page 240 social partnerships for the delivery of services, provincial youth parliaments, and even a digital game on youth and local politics.

My experience of working with young people in India for the last 20 years, as well as my postgraduate Youth and Community work studies in National University of Ireland Maynooth and my ongoing PhD research in ‘youth policy in Ireland and India; a comparative study’, have enabled me to link theory to practice and to reflect on my values as a youth worker and on my own practice. For me, youth work is about starting where young people are at. I believe that young people should have meaningful participation and a sense of ownership over their project. Moreover, young people have a right to be listened to and given a voice.

Conclusion

Youths according to the dictionary definition, is seen as “the state or time of being young young men and women”(Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary, Current English, 2001). In current times, it would appear that the majority of our youths are on the edge of reason and good conduct. Rather than exploring the opportunities for securing better lives, facing the challenges of a rapidly changing world, and thinking about the future of their nation, it is quite disappointing that the majority of our youths know more of how to showcase anti-social behaviour. It is shocking to realize that the constructive attitudes of youths in traditional society of Nigeria have gone with the wind (Aghahowa, 2006). Interestingly, governments at all level of governance, parents, guardians and all the stakeholders in our youth developmental process are finally waking up to the realities that the surprisingly negative attitudes of our youths can be traced to the fact that we have tens of millions of unemployed Nigerian youths, and millions others living in abject poverty, having seen the four walls of Universities.

Although there is no consensus definition of politics, its usage is very limited in time and space to certain lands of relatively liberal, pluralistic societies, which allow relatively open debate. That is, politics occurs where people disagree about distribution of means and have, at least some procedures for the resolution of such disagreement. The implication of the above analysis of politics for our discourse in this paper is that the youths in Nigeria have the rights and duties to agree and disagree openly about what goes on in the Nigerian state (World Youth Report, 2003). The growing commitment to the involvement of the youth in global development process is a clear recognition of their potentials as change agents within the civil society.

This awareness has attracted scholarly attention in an attempt to clarify and articulate a conceptual category for youth. In most literatures, scholars have often employed the criterion of age to define the youth. However, sociological studies have shown that this criterion is fluid and therefore vary from one society to another. The role of youth in Indian politics is dynamic, transformative, and indispensable for the advancement of democracy and societal progress. Through historical analysis, it's evident that youth have played pivotal roles in shaping India's political landscape, from the struggle for independence to contemporary movements for social justice and reform. Today, with India's substantial youth demographic, the active involvement of young people in politics serves as a powerful catalyst for change, driving policy agendas, electoral dynamics, and societal discourse. Despite facing challenges such as institutional barriers, generational divides, and socio-economic disparities, young Indians continue to assert their voices and advocate for a more inclusive and responsive governance framework. The influence of youth in policy making extends beyond specific policy proposals, encompassing broader systemic changes that challenge established norms and power structures. Moving forward, it is imperative for policymakers, civil society organizations, and political leaders to recognize and harness the potential of youth engagement in Indian politics.

By creating inclusive platforms, fostering intergenerational dialogue, and empowering young leaders, India can harness the energy, creativity, and idealism of its youth to address the complex challenges of

the 21st www.irjhis.com ©2024 IRJHIS| Volume 5, Issue 4, April 2024|ISSN 2582-8568|Impact Factor 7.560 IRJHIS2404024 | International Research Journal of Humanities and Interdisciplinary Studies (IRJHIS) | 21st century and build a more vibrant, resilient, and equitable democracy. In essence, the active involvement of youth in Indian politics is not merely a demographic reality but a transformative force driving positive change and shaping the nation's democratic future. As India continues its journey towards progress and development, the contributions of its young people will be instrumental in realizing the aspirations of a progressive and inclusive society. While discussing the role of youths in contemporary political participation and development, there are certain underpinning assumptions (Suleiman, 2006).

Firstly, we are assuming a political system that is endowed with a significant proportion of its youthful population who are highly informed and consensitized. Secondly, we are also assuming an organized youth with clearly defined objectives and a variety of legitimate methods to make input in the political process. Thirdly, we are assuming a political system with sufficient public space that allows for unfettered citizens participation and robust engagement in the governance process. Meanwhile, the degree of these variables in the Indian political system is at best measured and sometimes highly debatable, it has been observed generally that over twelve years of democratic experiment has created opportunity for actors in the civil society, or what social entrepreneurial scholars now call 'citizens sector' to take on their role in the political participation process (Bornstein, 2005).

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UNITY IN DIVERSITY : FARMERS' MOVEMENT EMERGED AS A SYMBOL OF HARMONY

Raju Bajantri & Dr. Mahalinga K.

Abstract

Unity in diversity is the lifeline of India. As the world's Largest democracy, India is exclusively positioned for its Diverse cultural, ethnic, religious and linguistic composition. Pluralism is the co-existence of multiple identities, social groups which is the fundamental characteristic of Indian society, is the root of unity among political, economic, cultural, geographical, linguistic diversity. Unity among diversity is India's precious gift to the world. It is a peculiarity of India that all those who follow different religions live in a sense of brotherhood, since the dawn of civilization. Likewise, it was the Farmers' movement that organized the struggle against the three Agrarian Acts, literally embodied the fraternal spirit enunciated in the Preamble of the Indian constitution. Through the united struggle of the Farmers' belonging to different languages, creeds, cultures, states and various organizations under the single symbol as tiller. The unity shown in the one and half year continuous struggle, demonstrated the unity in the diversity through the support of the all sections of the society, collective solidarity, brotherhood, communal harmony etc. Three agriculture laws which threatened the existence of breadwinners who forced the government to withdraw the Acts. It's the second major struggle after the freedom fight, through this, social movements became a symbol of the conscious society and demonstrated that the greatest contribution we have to give to democracy is to always be vigilant.

Key words

- 1) Farmers' Movement
 - 2) Agrarian Acts
 - 3) Fraternity
 - 4) Unity
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INTRODUCTION

The food giver of the whole world is facing thousands of hardships today. Although agriculture is the root of the civilization, starting from the rule of monarchies to today's democracy, there is no end to the hardships of the breadwinners. The price of every commodity is decided by the producer, but the prices of crops are decided in the market, in the hands of brokers with consent of the government, so Farmers' do not get any specific price. Despite of drought and floods, unaffordable agricultural equipments, expensive production costs etc farmers' are presenting their demand for minimum support price before every government and perpetual entreaties for set an appropriate support price for the crops they grow and solve the problems of the farmers. Between 1995 to 2016 more than 6 lakh farmers' were committed suicide.

On June 5 2020, the central government enacted three new Agriculture Acts through ordinance. Claiming that these laws were enacted to protect the interests of the farmers', unfortunately government enabling the laws that are favorable to the corporate powers. Farmers' of the country erupted against these Acts and almost one and half years, at Delhi borders they have protested to revoke those acts which were fatal to the peasantry. Social movements act as vanguard in people's democracy, The laws made by the parliament should represent the aspirations of the people. An important event of the first half of 21st century, the farmers' movement, from the beginning till the end, sowed awareness among the fighters, through unity, transparency, free food services, creation of alternative media etc. More than 550 farmers' organizations came together under the "Samyukta Kisan Morcha". This struggle preached unity in diversity and message given to the society is harmony. In this article the the essence of unity

achieved by different farmers' organizations, belonging to different caste, class, gender, province's etc is discussed.

OBJECTIVS OF THE STUY

The present study aims to explore how unity arose in diversity that underlies the Indian heritage. Involving all sections of the society, this struggle showed the path to future movements through sense of fraternity, creative activities, free food to all, spirit of service.

RESEARCH METHOD

The article uses a qualitative method of study. For the purpose of analysis qualitative content analysis has been undertaken. The study relies on secondary data sources.

DISCUSSION

In India there have been Dalit Movement, Backward Classes Movement, Women's Movement, Labor Movement, Farmers' Movement etc are going on since long time against pain, humiliation, tyranny, despiration, violences, oppression etc. The movements are the symbol of the vitality of the democratic system. Farmers' movement is an organized movement, who have been neglected and exploited. The hardships of the breadwinners are increasing from time to time in all countries of the world. The peasantry, who have been oppressed for centuries in India, are now subjected to severe exploitation. As a result of adopting the policy of liberalization, privatization and globalization in 1991. If the governments had worked hard to protect the interests of the children of the soil as they are doing to protect the interests of private companies, the farms and wolud not have succumbed to the poison of farmer suicide today. 11,290 farmers and agricultural laborers committed suicide from 2019 to 2022.

Farm suicides as per NCRB report

Year	2022	2021	2020	2019	2018
Farmer suicides	5,207	5,318	5,579	5,957	5,763
Agri labourer suicides	6,083	5,563	5,098	4,324	4,586
Total	11,290	10,881	10,677	10,281	10,349

The hardships of food suppliers are incalculable, while farmers are demanding minimum support price according to the Swaminathan report for the survival of the farming community, the ruling government is trying to shirke its responsibility by privatizing the agriculture. On 5 June 2020, the central government enacted three new agricultural acts through an ordinance. The Act was passed by majority vote in the Lok Sabha on 17 September 2020 and by voice vote in the Rajya Sabha on 20 September 2020. These Acts were published in the Gazette of India on 27 September 2020 with the assent of the President on 24 September 2020.

Brief description of the three Agricultural Acts

1) Farmers' Produce Trade and Commerce (Promotion and Facilitation) Act,2020. Government's argument about this act is that farmers can sell their produce anywhere apart from APMC, so that farmers get more competitive prices. Along with this, farmers will be relieved from the burden of cess or levy being paid by farmers in APMCs. According to Farmers' union's and protesters this act destroy APMC system. As a result, around 700 APMCs operating across the country will be shut down. The government is trying to get away from giving a minimum support price. The entry of private

multinationals into the agricultural sector requires farmers and multinationals to enter into an agreement under a free trade policy. By which multinational companies achieve monopoly. Subsidies to agriculture will be completely stopped. Multinational companies deception of price and weight will increase. It also creates artificial scarcity by hoarding essential commodities and exploits the growers and users. Presently in the country through Food Corporation of India the government is providing free ration to the people who are below poverty line. Through this act government is systematically destroying the rationing system.

2) Essential Commodities (Amendment) Act 2020. This Act is also known as the Freedom of Agriculture Food Procurement Act. Government's argument about this act is private companies enter the agricultural sector and introduce new technologies, provide suitable stocks for farmers' produce, which enables them to preserve agriculture produce for longer and sell it at a fair price. According to Farmers' union's and protesters private companies will create artificial shortages in the market by arbitrarily hoarding food items without any controls and profiting more and more, while people's essential commodities like rice, wheat, oilseeds, pulses, vegetables etc are all monopolized by private individuals. The activists allege that through this act, the government will create a completely free market system and lose its controlling authority.

3) Farmers' (Empowerment and Protection) Agreement on Price Assurance and Farm Services Act, 2020. Government's argument about this act is private companies enter into agriculture and promise to buy the crop itself at a price by entering into a written contract with the farmer and priced competitively. According to Farmers' union's and protesters, this act has taken away all the freedom of the farmer and left it up to the private company to decide what crop to grow, what fertilizer, chemicals to use etc. The farmers are thus enslaved to contract with the private companies to grow what they say and sell it at the price they say. The criticism made against these acts is that these acts have been created by the government's attempt to facilitate the big private companies and escape from its responsibility by sacrificing the interest of the food providers. The movement started to repeal the three agricultural acts enacted by the government. In this way farmers' struggle broke out on the borders of Delhi. On 24 September 2020, farmers started protesting in Punjab. More than 550 farmers' organizations joined together to form an organization called "Samyukta Kisan Morcha" in Delhi, from October 27 started a non-violent struggle. The movement lasted for about one and half years and around 700 fighters were martyred. This movement brought down the government itself and forced the central government to repeal the laws it had implemented. On 21 November 2021, the central government revoked the laws.

Unity in Diversity : Farmers' Movement Emerged as a Symbol of Harmony

This struggle emerged as a movement involving all sections of the society including Hindu, Muslim, Sikh etc. farmers, agricultural labourers, zamindars, landless, wage labourers, women activists and common citizens of all religions. This movement is an example of communal goodwill of all religions. It was a movement that lasted for about one and half years and was a symbol of genuine brotherhood, which is the true symbol of India, unity in diversity. In this movement children's from age 5 to 95 old age elder's participated. Farmers who came from distance of 400 to 500 kms built the peasant struggle through genuine brotherhood and friendship by converting the plains into villages as the future of India rely on agriculture and the decline of agriculture will mean the decline of the country.

Creative activities

With the beginning of the peasant struggle, this struggle has maintained active activities throughout the struggle. The fighters, who came from villages about 400 to 500 kilometers away, converted the

highways into villages. It can be seen that the struggle is always active through poster making learning, exhibition, music programs, lectures, discourse, gym, art camp etc.

Spirit of service

In this movement it can be seen that the fighters mainly carried out all the work with a sense of kinship and free service. Doctors, plumbers, electrician etc. performed many tasks with self motivation. For example volunteers washing clothes for elderly, sorting torn clothes through machines, polishing, a well equipped hospital for medical treatment, massage machines for tired legs, service through medical camps etc. Similarly people of Delhi go to the places of the fighters on their holidays and extended their support for struggle by preparing roti, cleaning, supplying fruits and vegetables.

Importance of libraries

It can be seen that farmers' organizations have fulfilled the task of ideologically preparing the fighters through lectures, pamphlets, news paper publication, social media to inform everyone about the Act by setting up open libraries in this struggle, which preached the importance of literature during the struggle.

Langars : Free food to all

Mainly through two principles of Sangat (satsanga) and Pangat (co-eat) which are the essence of all religions and preached by Guru Nanak, without distinction of caste, religion, languages and mass cooking preparation with the help of machines that make 1000 roties per hour, using steam cooking machines provided the free meals to everyone who participated from the length and breadth of the country. These langars are centers of free meals which united all the fighters. People from different parts of the country have sent their grown vegetables, pulses, milk, fruits etc for this struggle.

Restraint

Despite repeated attempts to destabilize the farmers' struggle, the restraint shown by the peasant activists was unusual. Every moment the fighters were denounced as terrorists, Khalistanis, traitors, urban naxalites, agitating creatures, anarchists etc. The patience, solidarity shown by the fighters for all times indicated the path that social movements should take and the approach that those leading the struggle should follow. Attempts were made to end the fight by using tear gas shells, water cannons, lathi charge, pellet guns by the police. Also, when the main channels of media not broadcasted about the struggle, alternative media such as Twitter, Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube and a daily newspaper called "Trolley Times" published by a 29 years old activist named Ravikiran helped the fighters. It is an example of the indomitable spirit of the fighters who boldly faced many attempts to destroy the struggle through inhumane treatment, cutting of drinking water supply, cutting off electricity, building barricades with cement and stones etc.

Guidance for future social struggles

"Kisan Ekta Zindabad", "I Love Kheti", "Jai Jawan Jai Kisan" are the slogans and got this slogans as tattoos on their bodies are very common in the struggle. The lesson taught by this fight is, when the laws framed by the government which are harmful to the people, how to organize the struggle against such acts and what are the difficulties that the fighters have to face, to make the struggle successful,

mainly through decentralized and collective leadership with restraint, non-violent struggle, inclusiveness, service spirit, ideological clarity, transparency, active atmosphere etc.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) Government should hold open discussion with all the stakeholders before making any law.
- 2) Government should not ignore the referendum, which is the soul of democracy.
- 3) As driving forces of democracy non-violent movements should be nurtured.
- 4) Recommendations of Swaminathan commission should be implemented.

CONCLUSION

Farmers, who have been exploited for centuries, as a result of liberalization, globalization and privatization have been subjected to more exploitations, they opposed these agricultural laws implemented by the central government and through continuous struggle of about one and half years, those laws were repealed. If the Food security Act is repealed, the marginalized people of the society will have to face many problems. It also leads to agricultural crisis and environmental crisis. An export oriented free trade policy will be fatal to small farmers and agricultural labourers. Mechanization of the agricultural sector by the privatizers increase the rate of unemployment. The unanimous demand of the farmers' organizations is that government acting more and more in the interest of the corporate sector, privatizing the agricultural sector and thus monopolizes the agricultural sector, which gives a free license to the exploitations and elimination of the breadwinners. Government should not shirke its important responsibility of safeguarding the interests of the farmers.

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E-GOVERNANCE A NEW APPROACH IN KARNATAKA PANCHAYATH RAJ SYSTEM**Dr. Gurudath M.T***M.A. K. SET Ph.D., Faculty. Dept. of Political Science, Maharaja Madakari Nayaka first grade College, Chitradurga*

Good Governance has become an important word in the development literature, Conventionally, both government and governance go together as they are very closely associated but governance has acquired a wider meaning and scope. The Government refers to the formal institutions of the state and the monopoly of legitimate coercive power. Good governance signifies "a change in the meaning of Government, referring to a new process of governing; or changed condition of or dared rule; or the method by which society is governed". Governance is ultimately concerned with creating the conditions for ordered rule and collective action.

E-Governance is the use of information and communication technology to promote more efficient and effective government, facilitate more accessible government services, allow greater public access to information and make government more accountable citizens. It involves new style of leadership, new ways of debating and deciding policy and investment, new ways of accessing education, new ways of listening to citizens and new ways of organizing and providing information and service.

Meaning of e-governance

E-governance maybe defined as delivery of government services and information\ to the public by using electronic means.

It is also known as the SMART governance by using IT in the process of government functioning to bring about:

- Simple
- Moral
- Accountable
- Responsive and
- Transparent Governance.

E-governance in India:

The Government of India and several state governments have taken steps to adopt e-governance in many areas of Public Administration such as Public Services, Rural Services. Revenue and Police Administration, Social Services, Public Information, Agriculture, Commercial and Municipal Services, etc. The July 2002 EIU e-business assessment ranked India at 43. The Prime Minister Atal Behari Vajpayee said on August 15, 2002: "We will implement a comprehensive programme to accelerate e-governance at all levels of the government to improve efficiency, transparency and accountability at the government-citizen interface". The Cabinet Secretary Kama! Pandey observed in the National Council Meeting (an apex body of the consultative machinery of the Central government employees) on September 6, 2003 "in order to provide good governance there would be a gradual switchover to E-governance. A fresh round of simplification of rules, regulations and procedures is on the anvil".

Benefits of e-governance:

Following are the major benefits envisaged under e-governance.

1. e-governance is a tool for good governance.
2. It facilitates transparency in Public Administration.
3. It helps to make administration citizens' friendly.

4. It reduces the gap between the government and the people.
5. It simplifies the procedures, rationalises administration and restructures the administrative system.
6. It ensures accountability in Public Administration.
7. It reduces red-tapism and corruption.
8. It minimises paper work in government offices.
9. It provides integrated services and information.
10. It is known for better decision-making and planning.

E- Governance approaches in Karnataka:

Karnataka State has been witnessing and experiencing IT revolution during the last many decades with the establishment of Infosys, Wipro, and IT companies. In fact, Bangalore has been called as the "Silicon Valley" of India.

The assumption of power by the Congress government under the leadership of S.M. Krishna in October 1999 became a landmark in the introduction of e-governance projects in some areas of administration. In recent years the state has emerged as one of the pioneers in the domain of e-governance. "India: E-readiness assessment report 2003" prepared by the Union government has quantified the levels of achievement by each state based on six parameters, viz, network access, network learning, network society, network economy, network policy, and e-governance. Each of these parameters has been ranked on a scale of 6 to 1. Karnataka has got 31 points, while Tamil Nadu and Maharashtra tied at 30 points each. Andhra Pradesh has obtained 27 points. According to this report Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Maharashtra and Andhra Pradesh are "leaders" in IT. Gujarat, Goa, Delhi, and Chandigarh have been classified as "aspiring leaders" in IT. Kerala, West Bengal and Uttar Pradesh have been emerging as "expectants", while Madhya Pradesh, Haryana and Rajasthan are "average achievers". The "least achievers" include Assam, Jharkhand, Bihar, Jammu and Kashmir, Sikkim, Arunachal Pradesh, Nagaland and Manipur.

E governance projects in Karnataka

The following are the major e-governance projects initiated by the Karnataka government. Each of them is being analysed briefly.

Bhoomi projects

In the field of agriculture "Bhoomi Project" was launched in 2001. Rajeev Chawla, Additional Secretary in the Revenue Department of Karnataka Government, mooted this project. This project to digitise rural land records seems to have opened up new vistas of e-governance in the whole country. According to an estimate 20 crores have been spent on this project. It is designed to computerise and records of the farmers. This would not only eliminate manual entries but also help to curtail the manipulation of land records. Under this project –

20 million land records containing details such as ownership, crops, bank loans, irrigation, etc covering about 7 million farmers are computerised:

- All the 30 districts of the State are covered;
- 10,000 officials have been trained;

The Bhoomi Project has changed the entire system by compressing the data into digital format and setting up touch-screen kiosks in 177 taluks from where farmers could get the revenue document by paying Rs. 15 as user's fee

The project earns a revenue of 1 crore a month;

Khajane Project:

Treasury is another area, which has been computerised to a great extent. It has become a silent lifeline of the state government. About 1.80 sub-treasuries and scores of other related offices have been brought under networking. Transparency and accountability are being ensured in the management of public finances.

c) KAVERI (Karnataka Valuation and e-Registration Project):

It is the state's first public private e-governance initiative. It envisages zero spending for the government. Its aim is to computerise and put more than 200 sub-registers in the state online, enabling property registration within 30 minutes of document submission from the present 45-day time period. In October 2002, it received the gold medal for the approach paper at the 6th national conference on e-governance.

(d) "Bangalore one"

The state government has signed two agreements in November 2002 with the Microsoft Company for setting up "Bangalore One" - an online portal where bills for government utilities such as water supply and power distribution could be paid. Citizens can access the portal to check status, pay bills, and get information. Taking technology to the doors of Bangalore citizens is the aim of this project.

(e) "Smart School Project":

In 2002 the government decided to set up within a year "Smart School Project" in five divisions of the state in collaboration with the Microsoft Company. It will provide software solution, teacher training and IT curriculum. The Karnataka government received accolades from Bill Gates, the Chairman of the Microsoft Company for its performance in e-governance.

(f) Computerisation of Judiciary :

The judiciary in the state is making progress in achieving e-governance at all stages. Computerisation of more than 600 courts has been completed and they would be connected to the High Court through wide area network (WAN). The introduction of WAN through satellite, on-line management of court administration would become much easier, cheaper and effective according to justice G.C. Bhuruka, judge of the Karnataka High Court. Adoption of digital signature would further strengthen e-governance and mitigate the hardship caused to litigants. A litigant could access the document required at the court nearest to his place and get a certified copy without difficulty. This document bears the digital signature of the judge concerned. Once a judge or an officer subscribed his digital signature on an electronic document, it would not be possible for any other person to change or modify the document.

Problems and solutions

Like the Union and other state governments, the government of Karnataka state is facing many problems and solutions in the adoption and implementation of a comprehensive e-governance policy.

1. Low IT literacy is a big obstacle for the popularisation of e-governance. Many -officers, officials, majority of people in urban areas and rural masses are yet to understand computer application and its utility. This has resulted in a vast digital divide.
2. Cyber laws are to be simplified and codified.
3. Huge amount of money is required to provide IT infrastructure and to implement the e-governance projects. Because of this financial burden, all areas of Public administration are not covered at present-
4. Effective measure is required to look into the problems relating to logistics of installation, training of personnel, maintenance and supervision.

5. The mindset about the colonial administrative system needs to be changed among the people and officials. There is an apprehension that e-governance would result in downsizing the bureaucracy and unemployment.
6. Citizens are to be educated about the benefits and advantages of e-governance and its authentication.

Conclusion:

E-governance is a desirable new public management system in the 21st century. Therefore the government has to adopt a comprehensive e-governance policy and programme. Moreover the success of e-governance requires e-readiness, computer application knowledge. IT infrastructure facilities. Networking of Departments & Offices, change in the mindset, public-private partnership, a strong political will, e-governance vision and action plan. E-Governance is not about technology and investment in information technology alone. It basically leads to reengineering of the processes behind the serene that actually deliver the services.

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CENTER STATE RELATIONS IN INDIAN FEDERALISM**Dr. Veeryanaik L***Associate Professor of political Science, Govt First Grade College Davanagere-577004*

Abstract

India is a vast country with so many languages, religions and regions. India had emerged as an independent nation after a painful and bloody partition. Soon after Independence, several princely states became a part of the country. The Constitution declared India as a Union of States. Although it did not use the word federation, the Indian Union is based on the principles of federalism. We can see that all the features apply to the provisions of the Indian Constitution. The Constitution originally provided for a two-tier system of government, the Union Government or what we call the Central Government, representing the Union of India and the State governments. Later, a third tier of federalism was added in the form of Panchayats and Municipalities. As in any federation, these different tiers enjoy separate jurisdiction. The Constitution clearly provided a three-fold distribution of legislative powers between the Union Government and the State Governments.

Key words: *Federalism, Center, State, Government, constitution, Dual polity, Committee, Commission, Power*

INTRODUCTION:

Federalism, System of political organization that unites separate states within an overarching political system in a way that allows each to maintain its own integrity. Usually, a federation has two levels of government. One is the government for the entire country that is usually responsible for a few subjects of common national interest. The others are governments at the level of provinces or states that look after much of the day to-day administering of their state. Both these levels of governments enjoy their power independent of the other. In this sense, federations are contrasted with unitary governments. Under the unitary system, either there is only one level of government or the sub-units are subordinate to the central government. The central government can pass on orders to the provincial or the local government. But in a federal system, the central government cannot order the state government to do something. State government has powers of its own for which it is not answerable to the central government. Both these governments are separately answerable to the people.

KEY FEATURES OF FEDERALISM:

Some of the key features of federalism are;

1. There are two or more levels (or tiers) of government.
2. Different tiers of government govern the same citizens, but each tier has its own jurisdiction in specific matters of legislation, taxation and administration.
3. The jurisdictions of the respective levels or tiers of government are specified in the constitution. So the existence and authority of each tier of government is constitutionally guaranteed.
4. The fundamental provisions of the constitution cannot be unilaterally changed by one level of government. Such changes require the consent of both the levels of government.
5. Courts have the power to interpret the constitution and the powers of different levels of government. The highest court acts as an umpire if disputes arise between different levels of government in the exercise of their respective powers.
6. Sources of revenue for each level of government are clearly specified to ensure its financial autonomy.
7. The federal system thus has dual objectives: to safeguard and promote unity of the country, while at the same time accommodate regional diversity. Therefore, two aspects are crucial for the institutions and practice of federalism.

Governments at different levels should agree to some rules of power-sharing. They should also trust that each would abide by its part of the agreement. An ideal federal system has both aspects of mutual trust and agreement to live together. Though only 25 of the world's 193 countries have federal political systems, their citizen's make up 40 per cent of the world's population. Most of the large countries of the world are federations.

There are **two kinds of routes through which federations have been formed.**

- A. The first route involves independent States coming together on their own to form a bigger unit, so that by pooling sovereignty and retaining identity, they can increase their security. This type of '**coming together**' federations include the USA, Switzerland and Australia. In this category of federations, all the constituent States usually have equal power and are strong vis-à-vis the federal government.
- B. The second route is where a large country decides to divide its power between the constituent States and the national government. India, Spain and Belgium are examples of this kind of '**holding together**' federations. In this second category, the Central Government tends to be more powerful vis-à-vis the States. Very often different constituent units of the federation have unequal powers. Some units are granted special powers.

PRE REQUISITIES OF FEDERALISM:

There are four **Essential prerequisites** for successful federal system;

1. Firstly existence of a dual government,
2. Secondly, distribution of powers between center and the states,
3. Thirdly division of powers between center and states is through a constitution which is written and,
4. Lastly the federal system envisages an independent and impartial Judiciary.

Federal Characteristics in Indian Political System:

The Indian federal system of today has many Such Characteristics which are Essential for a Federal system, here are some of them,

a. Written Constitution.

Written Constitution with "A Preamble, 395 Articles, 22 parts & 8 schedules" when formed, It specifies the structure, organization, powers and functions of both the Central & State government and prescribes the limits within which they must operate. Thus it avoids the misunderstandings and disagreements between the two.

b. Supremacy of the Constitution:

Supremacy of the Constitution. The Constitution is the Supreme law of the Land. The laws enacted by the center and the state must confirm to its provisions. Otherwise, they can be declared invalid by the Supreme Court or the high court through their power of

c. Rigid Constitution:

The division of power established by the Supreme Court as well as the supremacy of the Constitution can be determined only if the method of its amendment is rigid. Hence, the Constitution is rigid to the extent to those which are concerned with in the federal structure can be amended only by the Joint action of the Central and the State governments.

d. Division of powers:

The Constitution divided the powers between the center and the states in terms of the union list state list and concurrent list in the seventh schedule. Both the center and the states can make

laws on the subjects of the concurrent list but in the case of conflict the central law prevails the residuary subjects. Which are not mentioned in any of the three list are given to the center.

e. Independent judiciary:

The constitution in apples and independent Judiciary headed by the Supreme Court for two purposes want to protect the supremacy of the constitution by exercising the power of judicial review and two to settle the disputes between the center and states or between the states. The constitution contains various measures like security of tenure to judges, fixed service conditions and so on to make the Judiciary independent of the government.

f. Bicameralism:

The constitution provides for a bicameral legislature consisting of upper house and lower house. The Rajya Sabha presents the states of Indian federation, while the Lok Sabha represents the people of India as whole. The Rajya Sabha is required to maintain the federal equilibrium by protecting the interest of the state against the undue interference of the center.

g. Dual polity:

The constitution establishes a dual politics consists the Union at the center and state at the periphery. Each is endowed with sovereign powers to be exercise in the field assigned to them respectively by the Constitution. The union government deals with the matters of the national importance like defense foreign affairs currency communication and so on. The state government on the other hand look after the matters of regional and local importance like public order, agriculture, health, local government and so on.

Division of powers:

Indian constitution (Seventh Schedule) contains three lists; Union List includes subjects of national importance, such as defense of the country, foreign affairs, banking, communications and currency. They are included in this list because we need a uniform policy on these matters throughout the country. The Union Government alone can make laws relating to the subjects mentioned in the Union List. State List contains subjects of State and local importance, such as police, trade, commerce, agriculture and irrigation. The State Governments alone can make laws relating to the subjects mentioned in the State List. Concurrent List includes subjects of common interest to both the Union Government as well as the State Governments, such as education, forest, trade unions, marriage, adoption and succession. Both the Union as well as the State Governments can make laws on the subjects mentioned in this list. If their laws conflict with each other, the law made by the Union Government will prevail. What about subjects that do not fall in any of the three lists, the Union Government has the power to legislate on these 'residuary' subjects.

Conclusion:

The interactions between the Center and the States are the primary characteristics of Indian federalism. To safeguard Indian residents' safety and well-being, the Central Government and State Governments must collaborate with each other. They work together to prevent terrorism, manage families, protect the environment, and prepare for the socioeconomic future. The evolution of the nation has been greatly influenced by these exchanges between the center and the states. The better Centre-State relations contributed to the improved national government, an improved administrative system, and the integration of disparate communities into society at large.

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ELECTORAL REFORMS AND INTEGRITY IN INDIA

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Introduction

Indian Constitution has set up a standard association to govern the polls in the nation, which is the Election Commission of India. The Election Commission of India is a Constitutional association that is responsible for conducting, regulating, and analysing the poll elections occurring in the nation. The Election Commission was formed on 25th January 1950.

The Constitution entrusts the responsibility to supervise, direct and control the entire procedure and machinery for election and also for some other ancillary matters, on the Election Commission of India under Article 324. At present, it constitutes the CEC and two Election Commissioners. The Election Commission has the power of superintendence, direction and control of all elections to Parliament and the State Legislature and to the offices of the President and Vice President of India.

There has been a marked increase in the total number of candidates contesting the elections. While in 1952, 1,864 candidates contested for 489 elective seats. Elections to the 18th Lok Sabha are being held between 19th April to 1st June, 2024. 8,360 candidates are contesting elections across 543 constituencies. 744 parties have fielded candidates in this election. Of these, six have been recognised by the ECI as national parties. 16% of candidates have been fielded by national parties, 6% by state parties, and 47% of candidates are independents.

Elections lie at the very heart of democracy. It is through elections that people in a democracy participate in public affairs and express their will. It is again through elections that power changes hands in a peaceful and orderly manner in a democracy and the authority of government gets clothed with legitimacy. Elections thus not only sustain democracy but enliven it as well. Holding of free and fair election is, therefore, a sine qua non of democracy.

India is both the largest and one of the most populous democracies in the world. This apart, in comparison to most of the developed democracies of the world, problems of illiteracy, poverty, etc. still continue in India as is the case with most of the developing countries. Its electorate is not only vast but also quite diverse reflecting the plurality of caste, religion, region, language, etc. of its social mosaic. Conducting periodic elections in the country by encouraging large-scale popular participation is a stupendous task.

Going by India's record in this regard, periodic elections as a means of smooth transfer of power have been a regular and successful feature of India's democracy in the past seventy years. Not only this, Indians have time and again reposed faith in elections as the most potent means of non-violent and peaceful protest against all acts of omissions and commissions of Government. Elections have thus become integral to India's democracy as elsewhere in other successful liberal democracies, the world over.

However, certain aberrations have come to the fore in the very working of the electoral system over the years. The need to address such disturbing factors have generated a debate on electoral reforms in the country. The Election Commission which is under the Constitution is vested with the actual power of superintendence, direction and control of elections in the country, has, from time to time, come up with concrete proposals/suggestions based on objective difficulties encountered in the conduct of

elections. Politicians, through the platform of parties and Parliament including its various committees constituted for the purpose, have given vent to their desire for reform. Governments have also undertaken certain redemptive measures based on the recommendations of various committees. The process of reforms as well as the debate in this regard have almost been an on-going process.

The need for electoral reforms was increasingly felt towards the late 1960's in India. Till then the electoral system had functioned quite satisfactorily except for few of aberrations in the form of some malpractices like rigging or violence which are rather small in number. There was one party rule at the Centre and in most of the States. But this scenario began to change after the Fourth General elections held in 1967. Regional parties and rule by coalition of parties began to emerge in the States. The emergence of alternative party governments in the State witnessed the accentuation of some of the negative traits and distortions in the political system which manifested themselves in a greater degree in electoral politics.

Election Reforms Committees

A parliamentary Committee was constituted for the first time in 1970 to suggest amendments to Election Law from all angles. But with the dissolution of Lok Sabha in December 1970, the life of this Committee also came to an end. Subsequent to the Constitution of a new Lok Sabha in 1971, Parliament formed a Joint Parliamentary Committee on Amendments to Election Law headed by Shri Jagannath Rao.

In subsequent years, a number of Committees viz. the Tarkunde Committee (1974), the Dinesh Goswami Committee (1990), V.K. Krishna Iyer Committee (1994) and the Indrajit Gupta Committee (1998) have been constituted to examine issues relating to electoral reforms. Apart from these, the Election Commission has also, from time to time, made proposals for reforms. Starting from 1970, the Election Commission has submitted its recommendations on electoral reforms in 1977, 1982, 1990, 1992 and 2004. This apart, political parties through the platform of all-party meetings have also suggested for electoral reforms. The 15th Law Commission was also constituted in November, 1977 for an exhaustive study of the Representation of the People Act, 1951 with a view to finding out and identifying the measures necessary in the direction of electoral reforms. The Law Commission has submitted its 170th report regarding reform of the Election System. In addition, Government has also initiated redemptive measures from time to time.

Proposals for reforms Recommendations of Law Commission The Supreme Court of India, in the matter of Public Interest Foundation & Others V Union of India & Anr- Writ Petition (Civil) No. 536 of 2011, directed the Law Commission of India to make suggestions on two specific issues, (i) curbing criminalization of politics and needed law reforms and (ii) impact and consequences of candidates filing false affidavits and needed law reforms to check such practice. In the light of this judgment, the Commission worked specifically on these two areas and, after series of discussions, followed by a National Consultation held on 1st February 2014, submitted its 244th Report titled, Electoral Disqualification on 24th February 2014 to the Government of India. The law Commission of India submitted its Report No. 255 on "**Electoral Reforms**" to the Union Law and Justice Ministry. Justice Shri.A.P.Shah, Chairman of the Law Commission of India presented the 201 page report after due consideration and deliberations with the stakeholders including of registered national and state political parties and extensive and in-depth analysis of various issues by the commission.

Following is the summary of the report on various issues discussed in the report

1. Election Finance
2. Regulation of Political Parties and Inner Party Democracy

3. Proportional Representation
4. Anti Defection Law in India
5. Strengthening the office of the Election Commission of India
6. Paid News and Political Advertisements
7. Opinion Polls
8. Compulsory Voting
9. Election Petitions
10. NOTA and the Right to Reject
11. The Right to Recall
12. Totaliser for Counting of Votes
13. Restriction on Government Sponsored Advertisements
14. Restriction on the Number of Seats from which a Candidate May Contest
15. Independent Candidates
16. Preparation and Use of Common Electoral Rolls

Election Integrity

There are a variety of competing definitions of electoral integrity, but electoral integrity can be defined as the realization of principles in the conduct of elections that are necessary to support the broader realisation of democratic ideals - **James and Alihodzic**.

Electoral integrity principles are :- 1.Equality of Participation 2.Electoral management delivery 3.Certainty of the rules of the game 4.Opportunities for deliberation 5.Equality of contestation

There is an ongoing debate over a single, universal definition of electoral integrity, but it can generally be defined as any election that is based on the democratic principles of universal suffrage and political equality as reflected in international standards and agreements, and is professional, impartial, and transparent in its preparation and administration throughout the electoral cycle.

Without electoral integrity, leaders and officials lack accountability to the public, confidence in the election results is weak, and the government lacks necessary legitimacy. Electoral integrity allows for peaceful resolution of conflict, open dialogue, debate, and information sharing among leaders and the public. Integrity depends on public confidence in electoral and political processes. It is not enough to reform institutions; citizens need to be convinced that changes are real and deserve their confidence. To ensure that elections have integrity, other factors outside of the electoral institutions themselves need to be taken into account and strengthened. Election officials, judges and courts must have independence that is respected by politicians.

The subject of electoral integrity has acquired immense currency with increasing recognition of the limitations of purely structural understanding of democracy. Whilst the existence of a democratic system is no doubt extremely important, it is not enough to justify fair and legitimate political processes. Existing literature on elections highlight a number of reasons for flawed elections, ranging from failure of administration of the electoral process, fairness of election administration, unequal access to the media and public resources, registration problems, vote buying, disqualification of opponents, unfair disparities in political campaign finance, violence, electoral laws and management and so on. Much of the burgeoning literature on perceptions of electoral integrity has examined the causes for between country variation in outcomes. However, one of the most under-researched areas in the literature on electoral integrity pertains to within country variations.

electoral integrity matters for multiple reasons, including for political legitimacy, by strengthening public confidence in electoral institutions, a sense of external political efficacy, and satisfaction with the performance of democracy; for civic activism, by increasing levels of voting turnout and civic activism, while dampening the propensity to engage in protest politics; for political representation, including by improving the electoral accountability and thus the responsiveness of elected officials for the delivery of private and collective goods; for security, by accommodating all groups through electoral channels and thereby reducing the underlying grievances which lead towards electoral violence, popular unrest, and civil wars; and ultimately for processes of democratization, including encouraging the macro-level consolidation of democratic procedures, norms, and institutions. By developing a new conceptual framework, measured by new sources of cross-national evidence, this

volume demonstrate the importance of all these relationships, thereby drawing attention to the reasons why electoral integrity is increasingly moving from margin to mainstream in the research agenda in comparative politics, democratization studies, political behavior, international relations and security studies, and public policy.

Conclusion

It is an accepted fact that the electoral process in the country has developed certain shortcomings over the years which need to be corrected. But this should be done through extensive debate and discussion and in a gradual and continuous manner. Successive Governments at the Centre have realized the importance of the issues relating to electoral reforms. Suggestions made either by the Election Commission or by the various committees on electoral reforms from time to time, have been regularly considered and also implemented. While considering the proposals and suggestions of reforms of the electoral process, it has also been underlined that consensus of political parties in the country is necessary. Government recognized that electoral reforms is a continuous process and it shall be the endeavour of all the stakeholders including Government, Election Commission of India, Law Commission, etc. to implement such proposals on electoral reforms on which consensus emerges, from time to time.

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AN ANALYSIS OF INDIAN FEDERALISM AND IT'S CHALLENGES IN THE MODREN INDIAN DEMOCRACY**Rajesh J K***(MA, LL.Bspl, LL.M)***DESIGNATION : RESEARCH SCHOLAR****ADDRESS : DEPARTMENT OF POLITICAL SCIENCE,
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Abstract

India is a one of the big Democratic country in the world. The Indian model of federalism may be one of the most interesting typologies in the world. This paper provides a temporal framework in the discourse on Indian federalism by outlining the history of the country's federal structure, from the birth of the Indian republic to these contemporary times. It shows how the Constitutional Mechanism works towards the Co-Operative Federalism and prevailing political factors in each of these phases served to strengthen the Indian federal discourse, despite the centralised constitutional setting of the Indian polity. The paper highlights the working of the co-operative federalism, Centre – State relations, it's Major Agencies for co-operation between the centre-state, the major issues in the centre – state relations, major issues and challenges to the Indian federalism in the modern Globalized era, and offers recommendations for strengthening India's federal design.

INTRODUCTION

India takes great pride in describing itself as the world's largest democracy. However, this democracy is meaningful significantly because it is encapsulated in a federal structure. While democracy represents the majority opinion, federalism accommodates and links it to the voice of the minority, landing a flavour of Social Justice. This ensure harmonious functioning of the entire system. The Indian Constitution is to be characterised as Federal Country with some Exceptions. It is having a federal with Unitary features or vice versa. In unitary constitution the power of the government is centralised in one government. In Federal constitution, on the other hand, there is a division of powers between the federal and the state governments and both are independent in their own Spheres. The differences between cooperative the competitive federalism is that Co-operative federalism the centre and states both works. In competitive federalism the states have got a independent power to exercise in their sphere, and tries to become unitary in their jurisdiction. When Dr. B.R. Ambedkar introduced the draft Constitution in the Constituent Assembly in 1948, he spoke of introducing a dual polity, consisting of “the Union at the Centre and the States at the periphery each endowed with sovereign powers to be exercised in the field assigned to them respectively by the Constitution.”

✓ MEANING

The term federalism is derived from the Latin root "foedus", which means "formal agreement are Covenant." It includes the interrelationships between the states as well as between States and the Federal government. Federalism is a mode of government that combines a "federal" government with regional governments in a single political system, dividing the powers between the two. Federalism means a system of division of powers between two government were both the governments act's independently, but coordination and co-operations among both government.

✚ DEFINITIONS

- ❖ **Professor K.C. Wheare** said that “the federal principle is the method of dividing the powers between general and regional governments. Each government within a sphere co-ordinate and independent. Existence of co-ordinate authorities independent of each other is the gist of the Federal principle”.
- ❖ **According to professor A.V Dicey**, “federalism means distribution of the Powers of the state among the co-ordinate bodies each originating in and controlled by the constitution”.

✚ FEATURES OF THE FEDERAL SYSTEM OF INDIA

India is a federal system but with more tilt towards a unitary system of government. It is sometimes considered a quasi-federal system as it has features of both a federal and a unitary system. Some of the Features of Indian Federalism as follows:-

- 1) **Division of powers** :Division of powers between the centre and states is the main feature of the Indian Federalism. There are three lists given in the Seventh Schedule of the Constitution.
- 2) **Supremacy of the Constitution**: The basic structure of the constitution is indestructible as laid out by the judiciary. The constitution is the supreme law in India.
- 3) **Independent judiciary**: The constitution provides for an independent and integrated judiciary. Judicial independence is the concept that the judiciary should be independent from the other branches of government.
- 4) **Written Constitution**: Written Constitution is one of the Main Features of the Indian Federalism. In the Constitution each and every thing of the Governments works is clearly mentioned and Described.
- 5) **Rigidity**: The Constitution of India is rigid because it cannot be changed by central or state government. It is rigid because the amendment procedure is rigid as amendment can be made by joint action of centre as well as state. Etc....

✓ JUDICIAL POUNDANCEMENT TOWARDS INDIAN CO-OPERATIVE FEDERALISM

The judiciary has used numerous phrases to describe this concept of cooperative federalism, though all of them, in essence, have the same meaning.

- In the **State of Rajasthan V/S Union of India, AIR 1977**, Honourable Supreme Court of India, it was coated that accordingly to Granville Austin, the constitution of India was perhaps the first constituent body to embrace from the start what A.H. Birch and others have called “cooperative federalism”. Chief justice Beg called the constitution “amphibian”.
- In the case of **S.R Bommai V/S Union of India**, the phrase “pragmatic federalism” was used. In the words of Justice Hhmadi “... it would thus seems that the Indian Constitution has, in it, not only features of pragmatic federalism which, while distributing legislative powers and indicating the spheres of government powers of state and Central Government, is overlaid by strong unitary features....”
- In the case of **State of Haryana V/S state of Punjab**, the Hon’ble Supreme court said that “semi federal” and in **Shamshare Singh V/S State of Punjab**, in this case the Honourable Supreme Court of India observed that the Constitution was called “more unitary than federal”.
- In the case of **West Bengal V/S Union of India, AIR 1963 SC 1241**, the supreme court observe that the Indian union is not a true Federation, the five essentials of Federal character is
 - I. the constitution must be written;
 - II. it must be rigid;
 - III. it must be Supreme law of the land;

- IV. there must be division of powers between the union and State governments; and
 V. there must be an independent and impartial to interpret the constitution and the law's.

➤ ***CENTRE – STATE'S RELATIONS IN THE INDIAN CO – OPERATIVE FEDERALISM***

The Indian Constitution's federal system divides all legislative, executive, and financial powers between the Centre and the States.

There are three types of relationships involved in the centre -states relations:

- i) Legislative Relations;
- ii) Administrative Relations; And
- iii) Financial Relations.

✚ **LEGISLATIVE RELATIONS**

Article 245 to 255 of the constitution deals with the legislative relation between the centre and states.

✚ **ADMINISTRATIVE RELATIONS**

The distribution of legislative authority has resulted in a shared executive branch between the federal government and the states. **Article 256 to 263** of the constitution deals with the administrative relation between the Centre and States.

✚ **FINANCIAL RELATIONS**

Article 268 to 293 of the constitution deals with Centre-State Financial Relations. Specially Allocation of Taxing Power.

❖ ***WORKING OF CO – OPERATIVE FEDERALISM IN INDIA AND IT'S AGENCIES***

The idea of Cooperative Federalism in India enhances the centre-state relationship as well as relationships between states and local governments. Cooperative Federalism in India reflects an ideology of a stable relationship between the centre and other units. It guides all the governing bodies to come forward and cooperate to resolve common social, political, economic and civic problems. Cooperative federalism is the horizontal relationship between union and states and shows neither is above the other. Indian constitution has incorporated instruments to ensure co-operation between the centre and states to ensure that cooperation is necessary for the proper growth of the country. Therefore, few are the listed provision in the Indian constitution which depicts the core relationship between centre and state. In India the co-operative federalism working through the constitution as well as its Agencies.

- 1) **7th schedule- Division of Powers**
- 2) All India Services
- 3) **Full Faith and Credit Clause – Article 261**
- 4) **NITI AYOOG**
- 5) **Zonal councils – 5 Zonal Councils**
- 6) **Regional Councils – 4 Regional councils**
- 7) **Inter state council (ISC)**
- 8) **Centrally Sponsored Schemes:**
- 9) **Central Council of Local Government**
- 10) **Inter-State Water Dispute tribunal.**

Etc.....

➤ ***NEED FOR COOPERATIVE FEDERALISM IN INDIA***

- **Promoting social justice**
- **Ensuring accommodation**
- **Ensuring stability and growth**
- **Contemporary issues**

❖ **CHALLENGES TO THE INDIAN FEDERALISM**

The major challenges to the Indian federalism in the 21st Century as follows,

- 1) **Over-centralization:** The Centre enjoys more power than the states, and the most important subjects of the country are listed in the Union List. This often results in conflicts of interest between the Centre and states.
- 2) **Regionalism:** A strong feeling of regionalism makes it difficult for the Government to ensure cooperation
- 3) **Limitations of Inter-state Council:** While **Article 263** allows the Inter-State Council to make **recommendations**, It does not empower it to **enforce** or implement them.
- 4) **Uniform approach:** The Centre, while framing policies, fails to take into account the heterogeneity of India. The one size fits all approach doesn't work in a diverse country like India. This makes cooperation between the centre and the state very difficult.
- 5) **Fiscal federalism:** One of the major challenges is the unequal distribution of financial resources between the Centre and states. The lack of adequate financial resources can hamper the ability of states to deliver essential services and implement development programs.
- 6) **Multi party system:** The states today have acquired sufficient political weight of their own through a popularised party system enabling individual seats to embark on to bilateral negotiations with the union bypassing the institutionalized bodies of collective policy framing that have proved to be ineffective thus lending and negotiator character to our federalism.
- 7) **Voice of separation , regionalism and Globalization, etc....**

🚩 **SUGGESTIONS FOR PROMOTING THE CO-OPERATIVE FEDERALISM IN INDIA**

- 1) The office of the **Governor** should be apolitical, and the terms of his removal should be altered.
- 2) Restricting the use of the **President's rule** under Article 356 to prevent excessive misuse by the Centre.
- 3) Extending the mandate of the **Inter-State Council** beyond advice and recommendations.
- 4) Laying down guidelines to prevent misuse of the **President's veto** of the legislation.
- 5) Including states when the Centre enters into any **international agreements**.
- 6) Equal distribution of financial resources to all the states.
- 7) **Empowering local self governments.**
- 8) **Strengthening institutional frameworks.**
- 9) **Strengthening Inter-Governmental mechanisms.**
- 10) **Implementation of the various committee and commissions reports. Etc....**

➤ **CONCLUSION**

A cooperative relationship between the centre and the state is the need of the hour. Without a Cooperative relationship, it will not be possible to move ahead in the present economic world. The various Technological advancements, economic and trade activities and external aggressions across the world call for a Cooperative relationship between the centre and States in order to provide stability and security in the country. The sarkariya Commission report has also emphasized on the creation of a strong Centre state relationship. Cooperative federalism is the means to achieving a strong Nation. There is requirement of giving greater flexibility and authority to the National Development Council by constituting it under the provisions of Article 263. Further, there should be greater involvement of the states in the planning process and greater coordination in rising the funds for meeting the demands of the developing economy, thus, a Cooperative relationship is developed by the creation of various

Council which works for the benefit of the states as well as the centre and also by giving full credit to all the acts throughout the territory of India.

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YOUNG PEOPLE'S CONTRIBUTION TO INDIAN DEMOCRACY**Dr. Syed Akram Ali**

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION: Youth have a vital part in the development of the nation. They are highly ambitious, solve problems and positively impact the country and other youth. They have the power to forge their own identities and advance the country.

INTENTION OF STUDY: This Article's goal is to inform readers on that young people play in Indian democracy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY: The purpose of this article study on secondary data gathering is to compile all of the information that is currently available about children

PAPER DISCUSSES: This article's discussion of the data enables examination of youth attitudes of governance and correction, trust in institutions. Support for democracy and political involvement and apathy. These results will offer crucial context for determining entry points at the national level for including youth in democratic governance initiatives.

CONCLUSION: The analysis conducted in this article paper leads to the conclusion that young people cannot succeed without the assistance of their families, communities, the government, and other young people. The young people can then bring prosperity and prosperity to their lovely country.

KEY WORDS: Youth, Democracy, India, Government

INTRODUCTION:

Since Ahead independence in 1947, India has maintained its claim to be the largest democracy in the world forth past 60 years. In any nation, young people make up the largest portion of the population. It is thought that developing nations with sizable youth populations could see rapid economic growth if they make investments in health care and education and uphold and defend their rights. The younger generation in India is quickly becoming a responsible. Segment of society. Which wants to see the governance shift? Young people are not afraid to express their opinions or to face the repercussions that may follow. The young people are also conscious of their obligations to the country and the fact that only they contain the capability.

With over 62% of its population in the working age array 15 to 59 years and over 54% of its overall population under 25, India is currently one of the youngest country in the world. In addition it is predicted that by 2020, the average age of the Indian inhabitants would be 29, compared to 40 in the United States, 46 in Europe and 47 in Japan. We have a demographic advantage over other nations, because of this. Today's youth are growing restless and fighting to eliminate the inequalities

Through general elections, citizens of our nation, India are fully free to select the representative of their choice. Every citizen of the nation who has reached the age of 18 has the freedom to cast a ballot or select the representative of their choice. Every 5 years the nations hold a general election when you can freely select your representative.

Young people have the ability to transform the country younger minds are more creative and innovative, which advances the nation. However Young people should be given enough chances to voice their opinions and propose policies for the country advancement. Youth are strong as evidenced by the large-scale demonstrations in Delhi for the justice of the Nirbhay case against corruption in India, and for Jallikattu at Marina Beach. Young people with new ideas, not ideals, will play a part in this shift to a transparent civil society framework that can Impact political governance for the good of society.

PURPOSE OF STUDY:

These articles goals are predicted on:

- ❖ To understand how young people contribute to India's democracy.
- ❖ The Youth play a crucial role in Indian democracy, if they are allowed to work however they like, they have the power to alter or perhaps revolutionize the way our nation runs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Secondary data collection is used to collect all accessible information about adolescents in order to obtain all significant data and information that must be processed in order to establish the content of this piece. All of the facts were gathered and extracted from many sources on various websites. To guarantee the quality of the material relevance, and ease of comprehension, the sources were carefully selected. The primary justification for using the secondary data collection approach is the abundance of diverse sources on the internet.

THE ROLE OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE DEMOCRACY OF INDIA:

Analysis of significant aspects pertaining to young civic and political engagement is provided. This has a significant impact on how young people view their circumstances. The UNDP Asia Pacific Regional Center has teamed up with Asian Barometer, an Indian research organization to analyze survey data on youth sentiments toward democracy around the region. The information enables examination of institutional trust, political involvement and apathy. Support for democracy, as well as how young people view governance and corruption. This result will offer crucial context for determining entry points at the national level for including youth in democratic governance initiatives.

In a nation's political structure, the democratic transition phase is frequently a particularly delicate time that if not handled and safeguarded could lead to protracted civil and political turmoil. Young people must play four crucial responsibilities in order to preserve the momentum of democratic momentum in fledgling democracies:

- a) Establishing and strengthening young structures capable of offering the youth population empowerment, education, and a democratic viewpoint.
- b) To avoid naively falling in to the trap of rebel groupings and being recruited by war lords who could wish to spoil that nation's political assessment.
- c) In order to enable organized youth engagement and a coordinated youth activity a youth led initiative was established.
- d) Since trust and cooperation are the foundation of democracy, it is important to make sure that young people are actively participating in its development both during and after the transition dialogue.

As a result, a young front can offer the kind of connection needed to establish a supportive atmosphere in which civil society and the government can effectively communicate and work together.

Given the existing circumstances, young people play a significant role in Indian democracy and if allowed the freedom to work however they like, have the power to alter or perhaps revolutionize the way our nation runs.

1. Young people cast their votes:

When young people see the power they possess they may also be able to bring about change in the Indian democracy. Young people cast a significant portion of the votes in every general election and some of them are first time voters in 2019. The electoral list grew by 45 million new voters. Together their might and the youth's capacity for decision making may usher in a new era of Indian democracy whenever and however the youth so desire.

2. Young people can take charge by participating in the campaign:

Running for office and embodying the change they want to see in the nation is another role that young people can assume with their bravery and innovative ideas, the kids can accomplish far more than what our existing leaders are able to offer. Giving young people the opportunity to lead the nation would be a welcome development, and this change could be maintained with the support and guidance of like-minded individuals. The nation would get closer to prosperity if there were less opportunity for conflicts of interest between the common people and the leadership.

3. Social media is one way that young people can communicate:

Social media and other platforms for expression one's opinions are becoming increasingly significant components of Indian democracy. Various leaders attempt to present a picture of themselves on social media, which could aid voters in determining whether or not they are competent leaders. In a similar vein, young people are not afraid to voice their opinions about the different candidates and political parties which shapes the public's perception of those running for office.

4. Young people make a decision:

Even though they are thought to be impetuous and frivolous. The kids have the ability to make sensible choices when they are in a pinch. The Children possess the capacity to disengage from the situation and base their decision on the viewpoint of the third party. Young people are brave and don't worry about the future unless they are certain of their choice. Because they are driven, young people consider the wider picture and make decisions based on what will benefit the entire country, not just themselves. Youth's methods can seriously question the ideas of anyone who does not think logically and reasonably because they are also unusual thinkers. Therefore, if young people begin to use their full potential, they have the ability to quickly seize control of Indian democracy and transform it into something that is very different. Given the provisions and the insufficiency of the government's activities, today's youth are already dissatisfied and will do everything in their power to usher in a new era of Indian politics when the time is perfect. In addition to bringing new leadership, stability, and a welcome change to Indian democracy, this move will alter how the world views India.

CONCLUSION:

According to the article, young people still exhibit strong democratic principles and have not stopped participating in civic and political activities. In a culture where they feel excluded from the political process, young people now participate in a variety of democratic activities that are relevant to their personal conceptions of democracy and citizenship. Recent protest, riots and protectionism in many nations may be interpreted as young people's response to a political system that they believe denies them full citizenship and their fair share of power. Young people are now able to express themselves in several ways.

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CASTE AND COMMUNITY BASED POLITICS**Laxmi Laxmana**

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Abstract

*The caste system is a predominant aspect of the social and political structure in India. Caste is the most ancient feature of Indian social system and it is a major factor in the structures and functions of the Indian political system. The word 'caste' which means race. People born in particular race have their separate caste. It defines all social, economic and political relationship for the individual. Caste is a notable foundation of social stratification in India. Indian politics is caste ridden politics. Caste demines the Nature, organization and working of political parties, interest groups and all political structures and there functions. The concept of a community has been central to sociological thought, representing one of the fundamental building blocks of society. Communities are social Units where individuals share common values beliefs and practices which foster a sense of belonging and identity among members. The basic objective of this paper is to analyze the caste and community based politics and how it's impact on the secular and democracy Nation. This paper concludes with a valuable suggestion to overcome these challenges.***Key words:** Caste, Community, Politics, Social stratification.

Introduction:

The Hindu belief says that the People are classified into four caste and these castes define what jobs they can do what duties and what privileges they have. These four castes are the Brahmins (priests or Teacher), Kshatriyas (rulers, warriours), Vaishyas (land owners, merchants) and Sudras (Servants) and the 5th group is the group of the Untouchables called Dalits. One of the Hinduism holy books the Srimad Bhagavatam has a part (7,11,35) which clearly says these castes must based on skills, qualities and activities. However in real life tradition, castes separate people according to their birth. Caste has influenced the policy-making of the government. The programs policies and declarations of political parties are made, keeping in view the caste factor. Even different position within a political party are distributed in terms of caste configurations. Caste plays a very important role in election and voting. Political parties select their candidates on the basis of caste composition in the constituency. The voting in elections and mobilization of political support from top to bottom moves on the caste lines. There are many political experts who consider the increasing influence of caste in politics as a negative tendency,not helpful in the development of democracy.

Methodology :Collected secondary data from internet, Newspapers, published papers and books.

Objectives :

- 1) To analyze the impact of caste and community on Indian Politics.
- 2) Interrelationship between Caste and Community in Politics.
- 3) To provide valuable suggestions.

The role of Caste in Indian Politics: The role of caste in Indian Politics can be specially discussed as following:

1.Caste factor in political socialization and leadership recruitment:In the process of picking up his political orientations, attitudes and beliefs he naturally comes under the influence of caste groups and casteism. Caste values and caste interests influence their socialization and consequently their political thinking, conscience and participation . He bets on caste solidarity to occupy and play a leadership recruitment role. Caste influences leadership recruitment process. This is particularly true of caste conscious people of states like Haryana, Tamil Bihar and Andhra Pradesh.

2. Caste based political parties: Caste factor is a component of the Indian party system. In India, there are so many caste-based political parties which try to promote and protect the interest of a parties, in particular, stand predominantly influenced by the caste factor. DMK and AIADMK are non Brahmin and non-brahmin political parties from Tamil Nadu. In Punjab, Akali Dal has a community identity. It stands influenced by the issue of Jatsvs.non- Jats All political parties in India use caste as a means for securing votes in elections.

3. Caste based pressure groups: There are so many caste based pressure groups in India which try to promote and protect the interest of particular caste and for this purpose they keep putting pressure on governments the Arya Samaj Sabha, Dharma Sabha etc. are such pressure groups Who work for the protection of the interests of a particular community.

4. Caste and nomination of candidates: The caste factor is an important determinant of electoral politics in India. While nominating their candidates from different constituencies the political parties keep in mind the caste of candidates and caste of voters in that particular constituency. As a result of this candidate is sure to get the votes of voters of his caste.

5. Caste and voting behaviour: In the election campaigns votes are demanded in the name of caste. Caste groups are tapped for committed support N.D Palmer has rightly observed that caste considerations are given great weight in the selection of candidates and in the appeals to voters during election campaigns. In elections caste is the most important political party. The candidates asked for votes in the name of caste and they raise the caste based slogan like “Jat ki beti Jat ko, Jat ki vote Jat ko”. Such slogans do have an effect on voters and they caste their vote in favour of the candidates belonging to their caste.

6. Caste as divisive and cohesive force in Indian Politics: Caste acts as a dividing and cohesive force in Indian politics. It provides a basis for the emergence of several interest groups in the Indian Political System each of which competes with all other groups in the struggle for power. At times it leads to an unhealthy struggle for power and acts as a divisive force however, it is a source of unity among the members of groups an acts as a cohesive force.

7. Caste and organization of government: The caste factor affects state government policies and decisions. The ruling party tries to use its decision-making power to win the favour of major caste groups. Regional political power for furthering the interests of the caste groups which support or can support their regimes. The constitution of India provides for a single unified electorate and advocates the spirit of caste free politics and administration. However ,people’s voting behaviour , their political participation, the party structure and even of the government decision-making.

8. Caste violence: Caste -based violence often finds its way into politics. The traditional differences between higher and lower castes become vigorous and have turned into a violent and fierce struggle for power in society. The growing terrorization of the lower caste by the higher or even intermediary castes has been becoming a part of rural India’s political reality. However , until today most of the caste-based violence continues to characterize rural politics.

9. The demand for reservation by other communities: The provisions of the reservation made in the constitution have proved counterproductive also as the non-scheduled castes, have also started putting pressure on the government to make provisions of reservation for them.

10. Caste and civil administration: The bureaucracy also gets influenced by the caste as mostly, the postings, transfers and appointments of public officials get influenced by the caste

considerations. In these days the interest of a particular caste are kept in mind while running the administration.

11. Caste and formation of a council of ministers: While constituting the council of ministers, prime minister and chief minister have to give representation to the members belonging to different castes in their state and in case they do not do so. The support of particular caste put pressure on the prime minister and chief minister to give representation to their caste. Thus, the role of community is equal to the role of caste in Indian politics.

The following points need to be looked for neutralizing the role of caste and community in Politics:

1) The basis of the reservation should be economic not caste so that all the poor section of society are benefitted to it. 2) The education system should be remodeled on secular lines. 3) Caste based violence must be eliminated through well-organized efforts. 4) Media should play a neutral role. 5) The recognition of caste based political parties should be withdrawn. 6) All schools must encourage community living by organizing community meals and all students should be included in it. 7) School textbooks should be carefully revised. The study material should teach the students that the caste system is made by man. 8) By promoting Inter-caste Marriage and by providing special offers for people whom do inter caste marriage can bring changes in the next generation people.

Conclusion:

In the end of the research paper we can say that caste and community have laid a strong foundation in Indian politics. It's indicates a form of inequality. Now a day's caste become more important for politics and politics also becomes more important for caste. Sometime political parties increase this caste system by using caste based slogans and other thing . It destroyed the social harmony and created violence in society. To the development of society it is very important to remove casteism. Government should try to remove this evil completely. All political parties should also try to maintain social harmony. It is important for the development of world biggest democracy. In our country, which is a secular country ,there should be an effective effort to bring politics without caste and community.

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ENERGY NEEDS, ENVIRONMENTAL DEGRADATION AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN SOUTH ASIA: A POLICY PERSPECTIVE STUDY

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Abstract

Energy sources are the most important commodities in the modern era. They are the drivers of nation's development. South Asia being home for vast population of the world (almost 1/4th) needs energy sources to drive its development momentum, the continues supply of adequate, efficient and affordable eco-friendly energy services is crucial to sustain a healthy lifestyle and it's also important to address major socio-economic challenges such as rural-urban divide, inequality, social disparities, poverty, hunger, health services and illiteracy. Lack of inadequate access to secure and affordable energy is hindering the progress of developing countries in South Asia. On the one side we have growing world population and people's increasing aspirations for an improved lifestyle on the other side we have Earth's limited natural resources. So sustaining socio-economic growth within the constraints has become crucial collective global issue now.

South Asian countries like- India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Bhutan, Nepal, Maldives are facing wide ranging energy and environmental problems affecting overall development of their countries. It's visible that the problem of environmental degradation affecting ecological balance in South Asia has its roots in its energy needs. The historical usage of energy, socio economic backwardness and old-techniques makes it even worse. The United Nations (UN) sustainable development goals are guiding milestones for all countries that seeks balance between development and preserving environment. This target of sustainable development can only be met by ensuring popular participation in policy formation and collective effort at national as well as regional level energy and environmental sustainability. In this paper we will see how the environmental degradation in South Asia is deep rooted in its energy needs and how can it strike balance between development and sustainability.

Key Words- 1) Energy needs

2) Sustainability

3) Environmental Degradation

Objectives of the Paper-

- 1) To identify the importance of energy sources as basic driving force of development activities.
- 2) To examine how environmental degradation is impacting the life of the South Asian countries.
- 3) To suggest some ways to strike balance between development and sustainability.

Methodology-

The current paper is descriptive in nature. While preparing this paper many books, articles, papers and web-sites are used/ referred. Most of its information is based on secondary data and information which is gathered from the concerned sources according to need of the research.

Introduction- Economic growth of any country is directly powered by availability and usage of energy sources. Energy sources are an indispensable part of economic development. Energy resources and their usage are intimately related to economic development. Energy resources play a crucial role in the economic growth of South Asian countries, where energy demand is rapidly increasing because of its increase in population and industrialization. The South Asian nation's energy landscape is diverse, some of the countries having significant natural gas and coal resources such as India, Pakistan, and Bangladesh and while Bhutan and Nepal possess large hydropower resources. The

usage of these resources is crucial for economic development, as energy is a fundamental input for various sectors of the economy like manufacturing factories, agriculture and domestic services.

The importance of energy sources -Economic growth in South Asian countries is directly linked to energy consumption. Industries depends on a uninterrupted supply of energy to operate machinery to produce goods and provide services to the citizen. The agricultural sector which contributes 18% to the GDP of South Asian countries, depends on energy for irrigation, harvesting, transport and processing. The residential sector's energy needs for lighting, cooling-heating and cooking are important for improving living standards and quality of life in the region.

Economic growth of the South Asian countries is highly linked with energy consumption pattern due to the essential role energy plays in various sectors of the economy such as industry, agricultural and residential needs. We need energy for increasing productivity, facilitating technological advancement and improving living standards of the people. South Asia needs energy for- Industrial Growth,

- Agriculture purpose
- Residential facility
- Broader Economic Development

In South Asia, energy usage is a direct indicator of economic development. Higher energy usage generally correlates with higher GDP of the nation and improved human development indicators. However, the relationship between energy and growth is also very complex, because it involves considerations of energy efficiency, sustainability and the eco friendliness of the energy consumption. For example- while industrial and residential energy demand increases, there is also a need for sustainable energy practices, especially in the face of climate change and growing environmental crises. Nations in the region have begun exploring renewable energy sources like solar, hydroelectricity and wind power, to meet the rising demand while reducing dependency on fossil fuels like coal and petroleum. This transition not only supports economic growth but also helps mitigate and adapt to the effects of global warming ensuring that development remains sustainable in the long run.

TheGDP of South Asian countries are dependent on energy consumption across multiple sectors. Industries need energy for production and transfer processes, the agricultural sector require energy for irrigation and processing moreover residential energy needs contribute to overall quality of life improvements. In such cases ensuring a reliable, affordable and sustainable energy supply is critical for continued economic development in the region. Balancing energy demand with environmental sustainability will be a crucial challenge as South Asian economies seek to expand and modernize in the coming years.

Environmental degradation is impacting the life of the South Asian countries.The transition to sustainable energy sources is essential for long-term economic stability and growth. South Asian countries have vast health and other issues related to environmental degradation. India and Pakistan are facing air pollution problem like never before. Maldives is at most danger because of global warming. Shrilank and Bangladesh are facing sever shortage of food grains. Renewable energy has more potentiality to solve all these problems. If harnessed effectively these can lead to more optimal energy supply solutions for the region. However, the development of a robust energy infrastructure, including regional power markets and energy trade, is necessary to leverage economies of scale and ensure energy security.

The South Asia Energy Sector challenges-

- Absence of a competitive power market in the region, with the exception of India, hinders the potential for electricity trade. Open power market could enhance opportunities for such trade.
- Lack of funds for energy infrastructure development. Energy sector needs a lot of investments to build infrastructure, the capital-intensive nature of power projects and transmission interconnections exceeds the financial capabilities of South Asian countries, necessitating reliance on international donors and funding agencies, whose support is often conditional and limited.
- Lack of a harmonious energy policy among the nations. There is an emergency need for coherent policies and regulatory mechanisms to promote and facilitate energy trade among the South Asian nations.
- Upgrading hydropower projects technology- Old hydropower technology is leading to increased costs and economic feasibility issues. These all barriers collectively underscore the need for strategic regional cooperation and investment to overcome the hurdles facing the South Asia Energy Sector.

Suggestion / Observations- There is urgent need to have a strategic regional cooperation agreement among the nations in energy sector. There is huge potential hydro power generation specially in Bhutan, Nepal and India, we must explore it in sustainable manner to meet the energy demand of the region. South Asia has huge potential in renewable energy. It should concentrate and develop solar energy, wind and hydro power projects. Region is highly vulnerable to climate change crises, it should mitigate and adapt eco-friendly sustainable practices in industry and agricultural field. Region should encourage competitive power market, there is need to have legal frame work in this regard. All nations should encourage and attract foreign direct investments in energy sector.

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THE ROLE OF JUDICIAL ACTIVISM AND DEMOCRATIC AWARENESS**Dr. Chetana S. B**

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Abstract

²⁴Judicial activism is a key element of democratic governance, where courts play an active role in interpreting laws and constitutional principles to address pressing societal issues, particularly when legislative or executive branches fail to act. This article explores the concept of judicial activism and its relationship with democratic awareness, focusing on how judicial intervention serves as a mechanism for social change, the protection of fundamental rights, and the promotion of good governance. The article outlines the positive impact of judicial activism, especially in countries with emerging democracies, where courts often step in to address issues such as inequality, human rights violations, environmental degradation, and the failure of other government branches to protect citizens' rights. It examines the role of judicial activism in promoting social justice, ensuring accountability, and safeguarding marginalized communities, particularly through public interest litigations (PILs) and landmark rulings.

However, the article also addresses the criticisms and challenges associated with judicial activism, notably concerns over judicial overreach and the potential erosion of the separation of powers. Critics argue that judicial intervention in policy matters can undermine the democratic process and disrupt the balance of power between the judiciary, legislature, and executive. The paper also underscores the importance of democratic awareness—where citizens are informed, engaged, and active in holding both the judiciary and other branches of government accountable. An informed public is crucial for ensuring that judicial activism remains in alignment with democratic principles and that it is used to promote justice rather than to overstep constitutional boundaries.

In conclusion, judicial activism, when exercised responsibly, can be a powerful tool for social progress, but it requires the support of an informed and engaged citizenry. The success of judicial activism is contingent on the balance between judicial intervention and public understanding, ensuring that the judiciary remains a protector of rights while respecting the democratic framework. The interplay between judicial activism and democratic awareness is essential for fostering a just, equitable, and participatory society, reinforcing the values of justice, equality, and democracy in the face of evolving social and political challenges.

Keywords: Judicial Activism, Democratic Awareness, Fundamental Rights, Social Justice, Public Interest Litigation

Introduction:

In any functioning ²⁵Democracy, the balance of power among the legislative, executive, and judicial branches is fundamental to ensuring the protection of rights and freedoms. While each branch has its distinct role, the judiciary is often regarded as the ultimate protector of constitutional values and the rule of law. Judicial activism, a concept that has gained prominence in many democratic societies, refers to the judiciary's active role in interpreting and applying the law to address pressing social, political, and economic issues, especially when other branches of government fail to act. In essence, judicial activism often fills the gap where legislative bodies or executive authorities fall short in safeguarding citizens' rights or responding to societal needs.

At the heart of judicial activism is the idea that judges should not be passive interpreters of the law but should take an active role in shaping the legal landscape to reflect contemporary societal realities. While this approach can drive significant social change and advance justice, it also raises questions about the judiciary's role in a democracy—especially about the powers of the other branches of government.

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²⁵ Democracy

Furthermore, for judicial activism to be effective, it requires the support and understanding of an informed and engaged public.

Democratic awareness, which refers to the understanding, participation, and engagement of citizens in their democratic rights and responsibilities, plays a crucial role in supporting the judiciary's actions and ensuring that the principles of democracy are upheld. An informed citizenry not only strengthens the judiciary's role by ensuring that its decisions are respected but also holds public institutions accountable for their actions. In this context, judicial activism and democratic awareness are intertwined, with each reinforcing the other in the pursuit of a just and equitable society.

This article explores the intersection of judicial activism and democratic awareness, examining how judicial activism serves as a mechanism for social change and justice, while also discussing the importance of an aware and active public in supporting democratic processes. Through this analysis, we will explore how the judiciary's proactive role can empower citizens, ensure the protection of rights, and foster an informed democracy, while also acknowledging the challenges and criticisms associated with this approach.

Review of Literature:

1. The Concept and Scope of Judicial Activism

Scholars have long debated the definition and scope of judicial activism, with varying perspectives on its role in democracy. Some, such as Alexander Bickel (1962) in his book *The Least Dangerous Branch*, argue that judicial activism is essential for safeguarding individual rights and addressing legislative inaction, particularly in areas such as civil rights and social justice. In contrast, others, like Robert H. Bork (1990), view judicial activism with skepticism, suggesting that it leads to judicial overreach, where judges make decisions that should be left to elected representatives. The literature explores how judicial activism has evolved particularly in the U.S. and India, with landmark cases like *Brown v. Board of Education* and *KesavanandaBharati v. State of Kerala* (1973) shaping discussions around its legitimacy and necessity.

2. Judicial Activism in Emerging Democracies

Judicial activism has gained particular significance in emerging democracies, where courts often play a pivotal role in shaping political landscapes and ensuring that democratic values are protected in the face of weak institutions. In India, judicial activism through Public Interest Litigation (PIL) has been instrumental in addressing issues such as environmental protection, human rights, and corruption. Legal scholars like UpendraBaxi (1985) have examined how judicial activism in India has helped bridge the gap between legal theory and practical justice for marginalized groups, while Marc Galanter(1989) has noted that PILs have made the judiciary a powerful tool for social reform.

3. Impact of Judicial Activism on Democratic Governance

Another significant area of research focuses on the relationship between judicial activism and democratic governance. Some scholars argue that judicial activism enhances democracy by holding the government accountable and ensuring the protection of civil liberties. Cass Sunstein (1993) contends that judicial intervention can safeguard democratic values when other branches of government fail to act. On the other hand, critics, such as Jeremy Waldron (2006), assert that judicial activism undermines democratic processes by circumventing elected officials, thus creating an imbalance in the separation of powers.

4. The Role of Democratic Awareness in Judicial Effectiveness

The literature also emphasizes the role of democratic awareness in fostering a healthy relationship between the judiciary and the public. Researchers like Larry Diamond (1999) argue that for judicial

activism to be effective, citizens need to understand their rights and the judicial processes that protect those rights. Increased public awareness not only ensures that citizens can engage meaningfully with judicial decisions but also helps prevent the misuse of judicial power. Additionally, Donald Lutz (1992) discusses how civic education is crucial in promoting democratic values, which in turn supports judicial efforts to maintain constitutional integrity.

5. Challenges and Criticisms of Judicial Activism

The literature also addresses the significant criticisms of judicial activism, particularly regarding its potential for judicial overreach. Scholars such as Aharon Barak (2006) suggest that while judicial activism can lead to positive social change, it may also threaten the separation of powers and the democratic principle of popular sovereignty if judges overstep their role. Research also highlights the potential for public backlash when judicial decisions are perceived as politically motivated, as seen in cases like *Roe v. Wade* and *Narmada Bachao Andolan v. Union of India* (2000). Critics warn that judicial activism may foster a culture of dependency on the courts rather than on the legislative or executive branches to make decisions on complex social issues.

Review of Literature

1. Judicial Activism as a Mechanism for Social Change

The role of judicial activism in promoting social change has been extensively discussed, with many scholars recognizing its potential to address gaps in legislative action. Scholars like Aharon Barak (2006) and Upendra Baxi (1985) argue that judicial activism becomes crucial when other branches of government fail to protect fundamental rights, especially in emerging democracies. In this context, courts are seen as agents of social justice, addressing issues such as inequality, human rights violations, and environmental degradation. This body of literature emphasizes that judicial activism can serve as a corrective mechanism when legislative bodies are unable or unwilling to act.

2. The Role of Judicial Activism in Protecting Fundamental Rights

A key theme in the literature is how judicial activism helps safeguard individual rights, particularly when political and legislative systems fail to do so. Authors like Alexander Bickel (1962) discuss judicial activism's role in interpreting the law to expand civil liberties, such as in landmark U.S. cases like *Brown v. Board of Education* (1954) and *Roe v. Wade* (1973). Scholars such as Marc Galanter (1989) emphasize the judiciary's role in championing rights for marginalized and disadvantaged communities, particularly through mechanisms like Public Interest Litigation (PIL) in India. The literature suggests that when legislative and executive branches neglect certain rights, the judiciary can step in to protect the vulnerable.

3. Democratic Awareness and the Role of the Public in Supporting Judicial Action

The literature also highlights the importance of democratic awareness among citizens for judicial activism to be effective. Researchers like Larry Diamond (1999) and Donald Lutz (1992) argue that an informed and engaged public is critical to the success of judicial activism. This awareness not only helps citizens understand their rights but also encourages them to engage with the legal system actively. A well-informed populace can hold the judiciary accountable, ensuring that judicial activism aligns with democratic principles and is used to advance justice, not to overstep constitutional boundaries.

4. Judicial Activism and the Separation of Powers

A significant body of work critically examines the tension between judicial activism and the separation of powers. Critics like Jeremy Waldron (2006) argue that judicial activism can undermine democratic governance when the judiciary oversteps its bounds, particularly in areas traditionally reserved for the legislature or executive. This critique is grounded in the concern that judicial

intervention can erode the democratic process, as judges, who are not elected, make decisions that should ideally be made through democratic deliberation. This literature explores the boundaries of judicial power and warns against the risks of judicial overreach.

5. Challenges of Judicial Activism in Practice

Another critical area of discussion concerns the practical challenges and limitations of judicial activism. Scholars like Robert H. Bork (1990) and Cass Sunstein(1993) point out that while judicial activism can address urgent issues, it can also lead to inconsistent or unpredictable legal interpretations, particularly when judges are perceived as politically motivated. Additionally, judicial activism may encounter resistance from political elites, the public, and other branches of government, complicating its effectiveness. The literature also highlights that judicial decisions, especially in sensitive social issues, may face backlash, leading to debates about the legitimacy of judicial intervention in policy matters.

What is Judicial Activism?

Judicial activism refers to the proactive role taken by the judiciary in interpreting the law to promote justice, especially when there is a gap in legislative or executive action. It goes beyond a traditional, passive interpretation of laws, seeking instead to adapt legal interpretations to contemporary needs. In democratic societies, judicial activism is often seen as a means of protecting marginalized groups, enforcing fundamental rights, and promoting accountability within government institutions. However, it can also lead to criticism when it is seen as overstepping boundaries, particularly by those who believe that the judiciary should remain neutral and uninvolved in policymaking.

Historical Background:

The concept of judicial activism has roots in several landmark cases around the world, particularly in the United States, where it emerged as a response to the inaction of other branches of government during critical periods of social change. Judicial activism became especially prominent in cases like *Brown v. Board of Education* (1954), which led to the desegregation of schools, and *Roe v. Wade* (1973), which expanded women's rights. In other countries like India, judicial activism played a crucial role in the 1980s and 1990s when the Supreme Court became more involved in public interest litigation, addressing social issues ranging from environmental protection to labor rights.

Role of Judicial Activism in Democratic Societies:

1. Protection of Fundamental Rights: Judicial activism serves as a tool to protect individual rights when the legislature and executive fail to act. Courts have played a key role in advancing civil rights, ensuring freedom of expression, and upholding due process.

2. Social Justice and Equity: Through judicial activism, courts have the power to address social issues, often by interpreting laws in ways that benefit marginalized communities. Activist judgments can thus correct social injustices and ensure that the rights of minorities are protected.

3. Environmental Protection: Environmental issues often require immediate action, and judicial activism has been a significant force in pushing for sustainability and environmental protection in various countries. Courts have issued rulings to curb pollution, safeguard endangered species, and regulate industrial practices that threaten ecosystems.

4. Accountability and Good Governance: Judicial activism ensures accountability within government institutions. Courts, by interpreting laws broadly, can hold government agencies accountable for maladministration, thus fostering transparency and good governance.

5. Public Interest Litigations (PILs): PILs are a vital aspect of judicial activism, particularly in countries like India. PILs allow citizens or organizations to bring cases to the court in the interest of the

public. This has led to the judiciary addressing issues like human rights violations, labor conditions, and environmental damage.

Democratic Awareness and Its Role:

Democratic awareness refers to the knowledge, engagement, and active participation of citizens in democratic processes. For judicial activism to be effective, the public must understand and appreciate the importance of judicial intervention in certain cases. An informed citizenry can ensure that the judiciary remains a respected institution in safeguarding democracy.

1. Promoting Accountability: With greater democratic awareness, citizens can better hold the judiciary and other government branches accountable. They can push for transparency in judicial decisions and demand explanations for significant rulings that impact their lives.

2. Supporting the Rule of Law: Democratic awareness fosters a culture where the rule of law is respected and upheld. When citizens are aware of their rights, they are better equipped to seek legal remedies and hold authorities accountable, reducing the need for judicial intervention.

3. Protecting Judicial Independence: An informed public plays a crucial role in protecting judicial independence. When citizens understand the role of the judiciary in safeguarding democracy, they are more likely to support measures that protect judges from political or financial influence.

4. Encouraging Civic Participation: Democratic awareness encourages active civic participation, which complements judicial activism. When citizens know their rights and responsibilities, they become more engaged in policy debates, which can lead to reforms without always needing judicial intervention.

Challenges to Judicial Activism and Democratic Awareness:

1. Judicial Overreach: One major criticism of judicial activism is the possibility of judicial overreach, where courts may intervene in matters beyond their jurisdiction. This can create a conflict with other branches of government and disrupt the balance of power within a democracy.

2. Lack of Public Understanding: Without adequate public awareness, judicial activism may be misunderstood or perceived as undemocratic. In some cases, activist judgments may receive backlash from groups that believe the judiciary is overstepping its bounds.

3. Political Pressures and Media Influence: The judiciary can be subject to political and media pressures, especially in high-profile cases. Such pressures may influence public perception of judicial activism, sometimes framing it as a political rather than a purely judicial action.

4. Access to Justice: For judicial activism to be meaningful, access to justice must be available to all citizens. Socioeconomic barriers that prevent individuals from accessing the judicial system can limit the impact of judicial activism and prevent vulnerable groups from benefiting from progressive rulings.

Conclusion

Judicial activism plays a critical role in modern democratic societies, where it serves as an important check on legislative and executive powers, ensuring the protection and expansion of fundamental rights. Through proactive interpretation of laws, courts can address social injustices, promote equity, and fill gaps left by other branches of government, especially in times when political or legislative bodies fail to respond effectively to urgent issues. The judiciary, through landmark rulings and public interest litigations, has demonstrated its ability to safeguard the rights of marginalized communities, promote environmental sustainability, and foster good governance. However, judicial activism is not without its challenges. The primary criticism of judicial activism lies in the risk of judicial overreach, where courts are seen as stepping into the policymaking sphere, potentially undermining the democratic principle of separation of powers. Critics also argue that excessive judicial intervention can lead to instability and unpredictability in the legal system.

For judicial activism to be effective and legitimate, it requires the active support of an informed and aware public. Democratic awareness ensures that citizens understand their rights, engage with the legal system, and hold both the judiciary and other branches of government accountable. A democratic society where citizens are empowered to participate in political and legal processes can prevent the misuse of judicial powers and ensure that judicial activism is used to advance the common good, rather than to overstep constitutional boundaries. The interplay between judicial activism and democratic awareness fosters a healthy relationship between the judiciary and the public, reinforcing the principles of justice, equality, and democracy.

In conclusion, judicial activism, when exercised responsibly, serves as a powerful tool for social change and democratic governance. While it faces significant challenges, including concerns about judicial overreach and political pressures, it remains an essential mechanism for upholding the rule of law and protecting the rights of individuals. The success of judicial activism depends not only on the actions of the courts but also on the active participation of an informed citizenry that understands the importance of judicial intervention in protecting democratic values. Ultimately, when judicial activism is coupled with democratic awareness, it strengthens the fabric of democracy, ensuring that justice is both accessible and effective for all members of society.

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THE ROLE OF ECONOMIC DISPARITIES AND POLITICAL INFLUENCE**Dr. Hanumanthraya S. R***MA, PhD, Principal and Associate Professor, Department of Economics, Government First Grade College, Bukkapatana*

Abstract

²⁶*This article examines the relationship between economic disparities and political influence, exploring how unequal distribution of wealth shapes political systems and outcomes. As economic inequality increases, the political power of the wealthy becomes more pronounced, often distorting democratic processes and prioritizing the interests of the affluent over the general populace. The article reviews existing literature on the impact of economic inequality on political representation, drawing on key studies from political science and economics to analyze how wealth inequality leads to the concentration of political power. It also highlights the role of campaign finance and lobbying in reinforcing this power imbalance, with wealthier individuals and organizations disproportionately influencing policy decisions. The social and economic consequences of this dynamic are discussed, with particular emphasis on how inequality fosters political alienation, social unrest, and economic stagnation. Additionally, the article explores the global dimensions of economic disparities, where wealthier nations exert significant influence over international institutions, leaving developing countries at a disadvantage. Finally, the article proposes several policy recommendations to address these issues, including reforms to campaign finance, progressive taxation, and public investment in education and healthcare. The conclusion emphasizes the need for comprehensive reforms to restore democratic legitimacy, foster social cohesion, and ensure more equitable economic growth, highlighting that reducing economic disparities and political influence can lead to a more just and prosperous society.*

Keywords: *Economic inequality, political influence, campaign finance, social unrest, democratic legitimacy.*

Introduction:

Economic disparities²⁷, or the unequal distribution of wealth and resources within a society, has long been a central issue in political discourse. As wealth becomes increasingly concentrated in the hands of a few, the influence of economic elites on political decision-making grows, often to the detriment of broader societal interests. This dynamic creates a feedback loop where wealth inequality perpetuates political power imbalances, exacerbating social divides and hindering democratic processes. The growing divide between the rich and poor not only affects individuals' quality of life but also undermines the integrity of democratic institutions, as political power becomes more concentrated among the wealthy and powerful.

The relationship between economic inequality and political influence is a complex and multifaceted issue. On one hand, economic disparities enable affluent individuals, corporations, and interest groups to exert significant sway over public policy through lobbying, campaign contributions, and other forms of political involvement. This influence, in turn, can lead to policies that prioritize the needs of the wealthy while neglecting the broader population. On the other hand, the erosion of democratic processes—caused by the overrepresentation of economic elites—can deepen social inequality, fuel public dissatisfaction, and even lead to social unrest.

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²⁷ Economic disparities

This article explores the critical role that economic disparities and political influence play in shaping societal outcomes. It examines how wealth inequality affects political power, the implications for democracy, and the resulting consequences for social cohesion and economic growth. By understanding how economic disparities and political influence are interlinked, we can begin to address the structural issues that perpetuate inequality and work toward creating a more just and equitable society.

Review of Literature:

1. Economic Inequality and Political Influence

Numerous studies have highlighted the direct relationship between economic inequality and the concentration of political power. In their seminal work, *Unequal Democracy*, political scientist Larry M. Bartels (2008) argues that rising economic inequality leads to a political system where the interests of the wealthy dominate, often at the expense of the broader population. Research by Gilens and Page (2014) further supports this notion, revealing that economic elites and organized interest groups have a disproportionate influence on U.S. policymaking, while the preferences of average citizens have little to no impact on policy outcomes. This pattern suggests that economic inequality not only harms social equity but also distorts democratic representation by empowering a narrow group of affluent individuals.

2. The Role of Campaign Finance in Political Power

The role of money in ²⁸politics is frequently discussed in the context of economic disparities influencing political outcomes. According to Robert C. Smith (2016), campaign finance reform—or the lack thereof—has contributed significantly to the entrenchment of economic power in political systems. The ability of wealthy individuals and corporations to make substantial political donations through Super PACs and other mechanisms results in an electoral system where political candidates become financially beholden to the elite, further perpetuating inequality. Smith's analysis demonstrates how the *Citizens United* ruling in 2010 allowed for unprecedented spending in U.S. elections, amplifying the voices of the wealthy while marginalizing less affluent voters and reinforcing existing economic disparities.

3. Economic Inequality and Democratic Backsliding

The impact of economic inequality on democratic stability has been a subject of growing concern in recent literature. In *The Origins of Political Order* (2011), Francis Fukuyama suggests that a concentration of wealth often leads to a breakdown of democratic institutions, as elites use their economic power to influence policymaking and protect their interests, eroding the political will of the broader populace. Other scholars, such as Piketty (2014) in *Capital in the Twenty-First Century*, argue that economic inequality fosters a sense of political alienation, with less affluent citizens losing trust in democratic processes and institutions. This sense of alienation can fuel populist movements, protests, and, in extreme cases, violent uprisings, posing a threat to political stability.

4. Social and Economic Consequences of Inequality

The social and economic impacts of economic disparities are significant, with several studies exploring how inequality stifles overall economic growth. Wilkinson and Pickett (2009) in *The Spirit Level* argue that more equal societies tend to experience better social outcomes, such as improved health, lower crime rates, and higher levels of education. On the other hand, countries with high levels of inequality suffer from greater social unrest, weaker social mobility, and more pronounced economic stagnation.

²⁸ Politics

This body of literature emphasizes how economic inequality not only limits opportunities for the poor but also hampers the overall prosperity of nations by undermining the development of human capital.

5. Global Economic Disparities and Political Power

At the global level, the influence of wealthy nations in shaping international political and economic policies has been widely discussed. According to Joseph Stiglitz (2002) in *Globalization and Its Discontents*, global economic institutions such as the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) often prioritize the interests of wealthy countries, leading to policies that exacerbate inequalities between nations. This literature suggests that the economic and political influence of wealthy nations in international negotiations can leave developing countries at a disadvantage, as policies often fail to address the needs of the most vulnerable populations. Moreover, the lack of political representation for poorer nations in these global institutions further reinforces the disparities between rich and poor countries.

Methodology:

1. Literature Review and Qualitative Analysis

The primary method used in this article is a comprehensive literature review, synthesizing key studies from political science, economics, and sociology. This review focuses on examining existing research on the relationship between economic inequality and political influence, exploring theoretical frameworks and empirical findings from various scholars. Key texts from Bartels (2008), Gilens and Page (2014), Piketty (2014), and others were reviewed to identify common themes, patterns, and gaps in the existing literature regarding how economic disparities shape political processes and social outcomes.

2. Case Study Analysis

To further illustrate the points discussed, the article incorporates case study analysis of specific countries, particularly focusing on the United States, where economic inequality and political influence have been particularly prominent. A detailed examination of key moments in U.S. political history, such as the effects of the Citizens United Supreme Court ruling in 2010 and the increasing role of Super PACs in electoral campaigns, provides a practical example of how wealth can influence politics. Similar case studies are drawn from other countries where economic disparities have shaped political systems, offering a comparative perspective on the issue.

3. Data Analysis of Income Inequality and Political Outcomes

Empirical data on income inequality and its correlation with political outcomes were analyzed, focusing on indexes such as the Gini coefficient to measure income disparity and cross-referencing them with political variables like voter turnout, electoral results, and political party alignments. This quantitative approach provides a more robust understanding of the structural connections between economic disparities and political power, using existing datasets and studies from organizations such as the World Bank and the OECD.

4. Evaluation of Campaign Finance Impact

A significant portion of the methodology involves analyzing the role of campaign finance in amplifying economic inequality's influence on politics. This includes a review of campaign finance laws, particularly following landmark rulings such as *Citizens United v. FEC* (2010) and their impact on U.S. elections. Data from the Federal Election Commission and other relevant sources are examined to assess the relationship between large-scale political donations and policy outcomes, particularly focusing on the imbalance of political influence across different socioeconomic groups.

5. Cross-Disciplinary Theoretical Framework

This article utilizes a cross-disciplinary theoretical framework that combines economic theory, political science, and social theory to analyze the relationship between economic disparity and political influence. Theories from political economy, such as the elite theory (Mills, 1956), are used to explain how concentrated wealth translates into concentrated political power. Additionally, social theories on inequality, such as those put forward by Wilkinson and Pickett (2009), are employed to understand the broader social consequences of these disparities. This multi-theoretical approach allows for a more nuanced analysis of the issue, linking economic disparities with both political outcomes and social stability.

Economic Inequality and Political Influence:

Economic disparities allow wealthier individuals and groups to exert disproportionate influence over political systems. This influence often manifests through campaign donations, lobbying, and other forms of financial support that benefit political candidates and parties aligned with wealthy interests. As a result, policymakers may prioritize the needs of the wealthy over those of the general population. This dynamic can lead to policies favoring reduced taxation on the rich, limited government regulation, and decreased spending on social programs, thereby exacerbating inequality.

One notable example is the United States, where political influence is significantly tied to campaign finance. Wealthy individuals and corporations can make large donations to political campaigns, effectively buying access and influence over elected officials. This process is often amplified by super PACs (political action committees) that can raise and spend unlimited amounts of money to advocate for or against political candidates, skewing the political landscape in favor of affluent interests.

Impact on Democracy:

Economic disparities and concentrated political influence pose a threat to democratic principles. In a true democracy, each citizen's vote should carry equal weight, allowing all voices to be heard equally. However, economic inequality can distort this ideal by enabling wealthier individuals and groups to have a louder voice in policy decisions. When political influence is bought rather than earned, it undermines the legitimacy of democratic systems and reduces public trust in government institutions. Voter suppression and disenfranchisement can further exacerbate these issues. For instance, low-income populations may face barriers to voting, such as restrictive ID laws, long wait times, and limited polling locations in their neighborhoods. These obstacles, combined with the power of wealthier individuals to shape policies, create a cycle in which economic disparities reduce political participation and perpetuate the influence of the elite.

Consequences for Social Cohesion and Economic Growth:

Economic disparities and political influence contribute to social divisions, as those who feel left behind become increasingly disillusioned with the political system. This disillusionment can foster populist movements, protests, and in some cases, violent uprisings. Social unrest is often more common in countries with high levels of inequality, where marginalized groups feel they have no voice or power within the political system.

Economic inequality also negatively impacts overall economic growth. Studies have shown that more equal societies tend to experience more sustained and inclusive economic growth. Inequality can lead to limited access to education, healthcare, and job opportunities, which in turn stifles human capital development. This lack of access limits economic productivity and innovation, ultimately hindering growth.

Global Implications:

On a global scale, economic disparities between countries can lead to unequal influence in international organizations. Wealthier nations tend to wield greater power in organizations like the United Nations, the World Trade Organization, and the International Monetary Fund. This dynamic often leads to policies and agreements that benefit developed countries while putting developing nations at a disadvantage. Wealthier nations may push for trade agreements, economic policies, and environmental standards that benefit their interests, disregarding the unique challenges faced by poorer countries.

Global economic disparities also play a role in shaping responses to major crises, such as climate change and pandemics. Developed countries can afford to implement stronger measures and provide financial assistance to their citizens while developing nations struggle with limited resources. This discrepancy has led to criticisms of global inequality, as many feel that wealthy countries should contribute more to address global challenges.

Reducing Economic Disparities and Political Influence:

To address the negative impacts of economic disparities and concentrated political influence, policymakers and advocates have proposed several solutions:

- **Campaign Finance Reform:** Reducing the influence of money in politics by implementing stricter campaign finance laws, limiting donations, and promoting transparency.
- **Tax Reforms:** Establishing progressive tax systems that ensure the wealthy contribute their fair share, which can be used to fund social programs and reduce income inequality.
- **Improving Access to Education and Healthcare:** Investing in public services can provide equal opportunities for all citizens, helping to level the playing field.
- **Voter Protection Measures:** Reducing barriers to voting and promoting civic engagement can empower underrepresented groups and restore trust in democratic systems.

Conclusion:

Economic disparities and political influence are inextricably linked, with each exacerbating the other in a cycle that threatens democratic integrity, social cohesion, and economic stability. The concentration of wealth in the hands of a few not only creates deep socioeconomic divides but also enables the wealthy to exert disproportionate influence over political systems, often at the expense of the broader population. This influence manifests in various ways, including campaign finance, lobbying, and political donations, allowing the affluent to shape public policy in their favor, often leading to laws and regulations that prioritize their interests while neglecting the needs of the majority.

The consequences of these imbalances are far-reaching. Politically, the dominance of wealthy elites undermines the fundamental principles of democracy, where all citizens' voices should be heard equally. Instead, policies tend to reflect the priorities of the wealthy, perpetuating a system where political representation is increasingly skewed toward the interests of those with economic power. This not only diminishes the quality of democratic governance but also erodes public trust in political institutions, fostering feelings of alienation, frustration, and, in some cases, social unrest.

Economically, the concentration of wealth limits opportunities for upward mobility stifles human capital development, and hinders long-term economic growth. Societies with high levels of economic inequality tend to experience greater social instability, weaker social cohesion, and less inclusive growth. As a result, while the wealthy continue to accumulate wealth, the broader society suffers from stagnated wages, limited access to education and healthcare, and decreased economic opportunity. This inequality ultimately limits the ability of a society to harness its full potential, both in terms of human resources and innovation.

Globally, economic disparities between nations amplify political power imbalances, as wealthier countries exert significant influence over international institutions and negotiations. Developing countries are often left at a disadvantage, unable to advocate for policies that meet their needs, leading to global inequalities that affect trade, climate change negotiations, and access to healthcare and education.

To address these challenges, comprehensive reforms are needed at both the domestic and international levels. This includes stricter regulations on campaign finance to reduce the influence of money in politics, progressive tax systems that ensure wealthier individuals contribute fairly to societal welfare, and enhanced public investments in education, healthcare, and social safety nets to provide equal opportunities for all. Additionally, strengthening democratic institutions by reducing voter suppression and promoting political engagement among marginalized communities is crucial to restoring trust in the political process and ensuring that all voices are heard.

In conclusion, tackling the twin challenges of economic disparities and political influence requires a multi-pronged approach that addresses both the structural causes of inequality and the systemic ways in which wealth shapes political outcomes. Only by implementing these reforms can societies move toward greater equity, stability, and prosperity, ensuring that economic and political power is more evenly distributed and that all citizens have an equal stake in the future of their societies.

Reference:

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Wilkinson, R., & Pickett, K. (2009). The Spirit Level: Why More Equal Societies Almost Always Do Better. Allen Lane.

This book presents evidence showing that more equal societies perform better in terms of health, education, crime rates, and overall quality of life, while societies with high inequality tend to suffer from a range of negative social outcomes.

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Stiglitz critiques the role of global financial institutions, such as the IMF and the World Bank, in perpetuating inequality and reinforcing the political and economic power of wealthier nations over poorer ones.

YOUTH PARTICIPATION IN POLITICS

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Abstract

Youth participation in politics is essential for the promotion of democratic governance, the guarantee of representation, and the advancement of social change. This investigation investigates youthful individuals' motivations, challenges, and influence in political processes. Youth are becoming more involved in electoral participation, social movements, and policy debates as a result of their increased awareness and access to information. The research advocates for reforms that empower the perspectives of young people in political spheres, to establish a more inclusive and responsive political environment that aligns with the aspirations of the younger generation.

Keywords: *Political participation, political attentiveness, and the younger generation.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The future of any nation, including India, relies heavily on the active participation of its youth in politics. Since India's first general election in 1951, its political landscape has been dominated by established parties. However, younger generations increasingly seek a political system reflecting contemporary values. Despite their enthusiasm for reform, many young Indians feel marginalized, their voices often overshadowed by established power structures. Politics in India is frequently seen as inaccessible, especially by educated youth, resulting in limited formal participation at higher levels of governance. However, youth participation is essential to shaping a more promising future for the country.

Young leaders bring fresh perspectives and energy, making them well-suited to address modern challenges and foster an inclusive democracy. Expanding youth engagement beyond voting—through mechanisms like reserved seats for young people in political parties and parliament—could balance experience with youthful innovation. It's time for India's youth to help shape the nation's future.

Youth and Politics in India

India's youth, aged 15–40, comprise nearly 49% of the population, making them crucial for the country's development. However, political engagement is low, with a report from the Centre for the Study of Developing Societies (CSDS) showing that 46% of young people have minimal political interest. Many lack affiliation with any party, driven by disillusionment with corruption, nepotism, and caste-based politics. This disengagement hinders their potential to contribute to the nation's future. To ensure progress, empowering youth with opportunities for active and structured political participation is essential for India's growth.

2. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

- Despite growing awareness and desire for change among India's youth, their formal political participation remains limited. While they engage in local elections and social movements, traditional political practices such as corruption and caste-based politics overshadow their influence.
- This study aims to explore ways to empower youth, providing structured platforms and mentorship to enhance their contributions to India's political and democratic processes.

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To assess young politicians' interest in building a smart India.

2. To evaluate the decision-making ability of the youth in politics.
3. To analyze how youth utilize their power and authority in politics.

4. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Melike Tekindal'sIt evaluates factors influencing youth involvement, constraints they face, and the role of media in shaping youth engagement. Additionally, the study explores dynamics related to youth voting, volunteering, and participation in youth programs and organizations.

Vinayak Verma'sstudy explores youth's transformative impact on Indian politics, highlighting their ability to reshape policies and promote social reform despite barriers like nepotism.

Sanjay L. A.'s(2021) study explores and suggests that youth may offer a more forward-thinking approach than traditional politicians, who often prioritize short-term gains. The study examines young Indians' interest in politics and their potential as guardians of India's future.

Impact of youth's political participation in 18th lok sabha and 2024 Ktk Vidhana Sabha Election :

Youth participation in the 18th Lok Sabha reveals limited representation in the 25-40 age group across most states, with only 66 seats out of 543 occupied by young MPs. Most seats are held by those above 41, indicating a trend toward older leadership in Indian politics, especially in states like Uttar Pradesh 37, Maharashtra 25, and West Bengal 22.

18TH LOK SABHA AGE- WISE COMPOSITION

State/Union Territory	Lok Sabha Seats	18 TH LOK SABHA AGE- WISE COMPOSITION		
		25-40 Years	41-55 Years	Above 56 Years
Uttar Pradesh	80	12	31	37
Maharashtra	48	5	18	25
West Bengal	42	4	16	22
Bihar	40	6	11	23
Tamil Nadu	39	4	14	21
Madhya Pradesh	29	3	11	15
Karnataka	28	4	11	13
Gujarat	26	4	9	13
Andhra Pradesh	25	9	10	6
Rajasthan	25	3	10	12
Odisha	21	2	7	12
Kerala	20	2	7	11
Telangana	17	2	5	10
Assam	14	0	6	8
Jharkhand	14	1	4	9
Punjab	13	2	5	6
Chhattisgarh	11	0	7	4
Haryana	10	0	3	7
NCT of Delhi	7	1	2	4
Jammu & Kashmir	5	0	1	4
Uttarakhand	5	0	2	3
Himachal Pradesh	4	1	2	1
Arunachal Pradesh	2	0	1	1

Goa	2	0	1	1
Manipur	2	0	1	1
Meghalaya	2	0	1	1
Mizoram	1	0	1	0
Tripura	2	0	2	0
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	1	0	0	1
Chandigarh	1	0	0	1
Dadra & Nagar Haveli	1	0	1	0
Daman & Diu	1	0	1	0
Ladakh	1	0	1	0
Lakshadweep	1	0	1	0
Nagaland	1	0	0	1
Puducherry	1	0	0	1
Sikkim	1	1	0	0
Total	543	66	203	274

Only 11% of MPs in the 18th Lok Sabha belong to the 25-40 age group, indicating underrepresentation of youth in India's political decision-making.

KARNATAKA VIDHANA SABHA IN 2024

In the 2024 Karnataka Vidhana Sabha elections, 6% of the candidates were aged between 25 and 40 years. 41 to 55 were 8%, and Above 55 were 14%.

How to Assessing the Decision-Making Capacity of Young People in Politics ?

- Assessing the decision-making capacity of young people in politics is essential for achieving inclusive governance. Young politicians contribute innovative ideas, fresh perspectives, and a sense of accountability that can challenge traditional political ideologies.

- However, their potential is often constrained by inexperience, limited access to decision-making platforms, and a lack of mentorship. By understanding their involvement in decision-making, we can identify their strengths and areas for improvement, which will promote leadership development and enhance their exposure to governance structures.

How Examining the Utilization of Power and Authority by Young People in Politics ?

- Examining how young politicians utilize power and authority in politics reveals their impact on governance and policy.
- Youth leaders often focus on issues like technology, education, and employment, mobilizing supporters and influencing political agendas.
- However, their authority is shaped by public opinion, institutional support, and party loyalty. Analyzing their leadership and decision-making helps determine whether they challenge traditional political structures or align with them, offering insights into the evolving role of youth in shaping the future of politics.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research utilizes a **descriptive and analytical approach** to investigate the involvement of young people in politics. It explores their **decision-making abilities**, the application of power and authority, and the interests of young politicians in fostering a progressive India. The study relies on **secondary sources, including scholarly articles, reports, and existing literature**. The aim of this research is to **provide a comprehensive understanding of the socio-political factors that influence young people's participation in politics** and to assess their potential impact on the future political landscape of India by integrating these resources.

6. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- This study explores the impact of youth on the political landscape of India, focusing on their ability to bring about positive change and influence democratic governance.
- It assesses the decision-making skills, interest in progressive political initiatives, and exercise of authority by young politicians.
- The research also highlights how youth engagement can improve accountability, transparency, and inclusivity in the political sphere.
- The aim of the study is to provide policymakers, educators, and social organizations with valuable insights into promoting political participation among young people through an analysis of secondary sources.

7. CONCLUSION

- In conclusion, active youth participation in politics is essential for building a progressive and inclusive democracy.
- The limited representation of young Members of Parliament in the 18th Lok Sabha underscores the necessity for increased youth engagement in decision-making.
- By addressing critical issues such as employment, education, and technology, young leaders can offer fresh perspectives and drive meaningful change.
- Providing mentorship and support will empower young individuals to overcome barriers, ensuring a vibrant political future that reflects the needs of India's youth.

8. FUTURE RESEARCH NEEDED

1. **Identifying Barriers to Success:** Explore financial, mentorship, and systemic challenges that prevent young people from advancing in politics.

2. **Impact on Policy Outcomes:** Assess how youth participation shapes policy decisions, highlighting the real-world influence of their engagement.
3. **Role of Digital Platforms:** Study the effectiveness of digital media in mobilizing adolescents and fostering political involvement.
4. **Comparative Regional or Cross-Country Studies:** Compare youth engagement strategies across regions to identify successful approaches for sustainable political involvement.
5. **Longitudinal Analysis of Engagement Patterns:** Examine changes in youth political involvement over time to understand trends and long-term impacts.

CENTRE-STATE RELATIONS: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES IN INDIA**Imamasab**

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Indian constitution being a Federal in structure divides the all the legislature, executive and financial powers between centre and states, but not the judicial powers. In India, there is an integrated Judicial system under the control of apex court (SC) to enforce both the central and state laws

In part XI and XII of the constitution centre-state relations i.e. legislative, administrative and financial are discussed.

1. Legislative Relations:

Federalism in the modern age is a principle of reconciliation between common interest and the need for local autonomy. Interdependence between the two sets of govt. is necessary for orderly progress and prosperity. Unity while allowing diversity, and oneness while providing for division is the outstanding feature of modern federalism. What is needed today is to make compromise between centralisation and decentralisation.

Articles 245 to 255, Part XI, Chapter I deal with legislative relations between the centre and the states. These can be discussed under the following heads.

1. Territorial extent of union and state legislation:

According to Article 245(1):

- A) Parliament has the power to make laws for the whole or any part of territory of India, (states and union territories). The state legislature has the power to make laws relating to its subject within its competence for the whole or any part of the state to which it belongs. The state legislature has no power to enlarge its territorial jurisdiction. But it is the parliament which has the power to do so.
- B) Under Article 245(2), the union parliament possesses the power of extra-territorial legislation (which the state legislature does not possess), in the sense, its laws govern not only Indian subjects within the territory of India but also Indian subjects (persons and their property) living and situated anywhere else in the world.

According to Article 246:

The union parliament has the exclusive power to make laws with regard to 99 subjects (union list). The state list includes 61 subjects over which the state legislature has the power to make laws. There is concurrent list which contains 52 subjects over which both the union parliament and the states legislatures have co-equal power to make the laws.

Article 247:

Under this article parliament by law may provide for the establishment of any additional court for better administration of laws made by parliament or for any existing laws with respect to a matter enumerated in the list.

Article 248 Residency Powers :

It is the power to legislate with regard to any matter not enumerated in any three lists. The constitution vests this power of legislation in the union parliament (Canadian model). Such power belongs to the states in USA and Australia. Such powers include the power of imposing any law imposing a tax not mentioned in any of these lists.

Article 249:

Under this article, (exceptional circumstances), the parliament is empowered to make a law on any item of the state list for a temporary period. If the Rajya Sabha passes a resolution by 2/3rds majority of its members present and voting by declaring that it is necessary in the national interest, such a resolution remains in force for a year but its duration can be extended for subsequent year for any number of times.

Article 250, Parliament's power in national emergency :

According to this article, while a proclamation of emergency made by the president is in force, then the parliament shall have the power to make laws with respect of state subjects. Such a law is applicable to the whole country or any part thereof in case of a National Emergency (under Article 352) or Financial Emergency (under Article 360) or President's rule (Article 356) in states. Such a law of the union parliament shall cease to have its effect at the most after six months of the expiry of proclamation of emergency, though, the centre may repeal or revoke it earlier.

Article 351:

Says nothing in Articles 249 and 250 restrict the power of state legislature to make laws on the subjects in the state list

However, under Article 249 and 250, any law made by state legislature in inconsistent with any provision made by parliament, it is law made by parliament prevail over state law.

Article 252 (agreement between the states):

If the legislatures of two or more states request the parliament to make a law on a subject in the state list, by passing a resolution, then the parliament shall have the power to do so. It is a legislation by invitation of the states. or consent

Article 253 (to implement any treaty or agreement):

Under this Article, parliament shall have the power to make a law on any item included in the state list for the whole of the country or any part thereof to implement any agreement or treaty or convention with any other country or countries (International treaties).

Article 254:

According to this Article, if a state law is repugnant to law of parliament. It is the law of parliament which will prevail over the state law. The state law will be void.

Article 255:

Says that "No act of parliament or a state legislature shall be invalid by reason only that some recommendation or previous sanction by this constitution was not given or taken.

So the above analysis makes it clear, that the union parliament is very strong, dominant and powerful to make laws with regard to the subjects mentioned in three lists.

Recommendations of Sarkaria Commission of 1988:

Sarkaria commission was appointed under the chairmanship of justice R.S. Sarkaria (former judge of the supreme court) in 1983, with B. Shivaraman and S.R. Sen as members. (former judges of the supreme court)

Commission made the following recommendations for promoting centre-state cooperation.

The following are the recommendations with regard to legislative relations.

- 1) Residuary powers of legislation with regard to taxation matters should continue with the centre. But residuary power other than taxation should be included in the concurrent list.

- 2) The enforcement of union laws particularly those relating to the concurrent list is secured through the machinery of the states.
- 3) The union should keep only that field of a concurrent subject on which uniformity of policy is essential leaving the rest of the states to the broad framework of union law. Wherever, the union proposes to undertake legislation with respect to a matter in the concurrent list, there should be prior consultation with the states individually and collectively.
- 4) Any law passed by parliament with regard to a matter in the state list under Article 252 should not be continued for more than 3 years.

II) Administrative Relations :

Chapter II of part XI, Articles, 256 to 263 deal with administrative relations between the centre and the states.

1) Article 256: Obligation of the states and the union: Under Article 256,

- a) The executive power of every state shall be so exercised as to ensure compliance with the union laws and existing laws which apply in that state.
- b) The executive power of the union shall extend to giving of such directions to a state as the Govt. of India deems it necessary.

2) **Article 257: Control by union over states in certain cases:** According to Article 257,

- 1) Executive power of the state shall be exercised in a way, as not to impede the executive power of the union.
- 2) The executive power of the union extends giving directions to the states,
 - a) to the construction and maintenance of the means of communication of national and military importance.
 - b) measure to be taken for the protection of the railway within the state.
 - c) to pay the states extra cost for the protection of their property or
 - d) to determine by an arbitrator appointed by the chief justice of India in the event of any dispute.
- 3) Article 258 Power of union to confer powers on states in certain cases: Under Article 258,
 - i) The president may with the consent of the govt. of the state either conditionally or unconditionally entrust to that govt. functions in relation to any matter to which the executive power of the union extends.
 - ii) A law made by parliament, which applies in any state, and relates to a matter with respect to which the legislature of the state has no power to make laws, confer powers, impose duties or authorise the conferring of powers and imposing of duties upon the state or officers and authorities thereof.

Article 312: Creation of all India service: Common to the union states:

Under Article 312, the council of the states by passing a resolution by 2/3rds majority of its members present and voting, empowers parliament to create All India Services (IAS and IPS) common to union and state govts.

According to Article 355, union govt. may take all necessary steps to protect every state against external aggression and internal disturbances. The idea is that the govt. of every state is carried on in accordance with the provisions of the constitution.

Under Article 365,

If any state fails to comply with any direction given in the exercise of executive power of the union, then the president declares a situation, wherein, the govt. of the state cannot be carried in accordance with the provisions of the constitution.

Article 356: In the event of failure of constitutional machinery in the state: Under this Article, the president is empowered to dismiss a state govt. (except Jammu and Kashmir) in the event of breakdown of constitutional machinery in it. The assembly gets dissolved or it may be kept under suspended animation (half emergency).

Apart from these, the union govt. has the power to give directions to the state govt. with regard to exercise of executive power in certain matters. It is thus evident that even in administrative sphere, the states cannot act in isolation rather they have to work under the directions of the central govt.

Major Recommendations of Sarkaria Commission to strengthen administrative relations: States always demand more administrative autonomy, so the recommendations are as follows:

- 1) Directions from the centre under Articles 256 and 257 and the application of sanction under Article 365 in the event of non-compliance must be measure of last resort.
- 2) Article 258 can be liberally used for the realisation of cooperative federalism.
- 3) Article 356 should be used very sparingly as a measure of last resort. President's rule should be proclaimed on the basis of Governor's Report.
- 4) A permanent inter-state council called the inter- governmental council should be set up under Article 263. It should consist of general body and a standing committee.

The general body may consist of P.M. as the chairman, all chief ministers and central cabinet ministers (members). The standing committee may consist of P.M. (chairman) 6 chief ministers (one from each zone selected annually) and 6 union cabinet ministers nominated by P.M. as members.

III) Financial Relations :

Chapters I and II of part XII Article 264 to 293 deal with the financial relations between the union and states. According to D.D. Basu,

"No system of federation can be successful unless both union and the states have at their disposal adequate financial resources to enable them to discharge their respective responsibilities under the constitution".

Our constitution has made elaborate provisions relating to the distribution of the proceeds of the taxes as well as non-tax revenues and the power of borrowing supplemented with provisions for grants-in-aid by the union Govt. to the states.

1. Article 265 lays down that no tax shall be levied and collected except by authority of law.
2. Article 266 says about the consolidated funds and public accounts of India and of the states.
3. Article 267 says about the contingency fund of the union and of the states.

Union Sources:

1. Corporation tax.
2. Currency, coinage, legal tender foreign exchange.
3. Duties of customs export duties.
4. Duties of excise on tobacco and certain goods manufactured or produced in India.
5. Estate duty in respect of property other than agricultural land.

6. Fees in respect of any of the matters in the union list but not including any fees taken in any court.
 7. Foreign loans.
 8. Lotteries organised by the Govt. of India or the Govt. of a state.
 9. Post office savings bank.
 - 10. Post and telegraphs, telephones, wireless broad casting and other like forms of communication.
 11. Property of the union.
 12. Public debt of the union.
 13. Railways.
 14. Rates of stamp duty in respect of Bills of exchange, cheques, promissory notes etc.
 15. Reserve bank of India.
 16. Taxes on income other than agricultural income.
 17. Taxes on the capital value of the assets exclusive of agricultural land of individuals and companies.
 18. Taxes other than stamp duties on transactions in stock exchanges and future markets.
 19. Taxes on the sale or purchase of newspapers and on advertisements published therein.
 20. Terminal taxes on goods or passengers carried by railways, sea or Air.
- 11) State Sources:
1. Capitation taxes.
 2. Duties in respect of succession to agricultural land.
 3. Duties of excise on certain goods produced or manufactured in the states such as alcoholic, liquids, opium etc.
 4. Estate duty in respect of agricultural land.
 5. Fees in respect of any of the matters in the state list but not including fees taken in any court.
 6. Land revenue.
 7. Rates of stamp duty in respect of documents other than these specified in the union list.
 8. Taxes on agricultural income.
 9. Taxes on land and buildings.
 10. Taxes on mineral rights, subject to limitation imposed by parliament relating to mineral development.
 11. Taxes on the consumption or sale of electricity.
 12. Taxes on the entry of goods into a local area for consumption, use of sale therein.
 13. Taxes on the sale and purchase of goods other than newspapers.
 14. Taxes on advertisement other than those published. in newspapers.
 15. Taxes on goods and passengers carried by road or on in land water ways.
 16. Taxes on vehicles.
 17. Taxes on animals and boats.
 18. Taxes on professions, trades, callings and employments.
 19. Taxes on luxuries including taxes on entertainments, amusement, betting and gambling.
 20. Tolls.
- Distribution of the the revenues between the union and states:
- III) A) Duties levied by the union but collected by the states (Article 268)

Stamp duties and duties of excise on medicinal and toilet preparations (mentioned in the union list). Shall be levied by the Govt. of India but shall be collected

i) in the case where such duties are leviable within any union territory by the Govt. of India; and

ii) in other cases by the states within which such duties are respectively leviable.

B) Taxes levied and collected by the union but assigned to the state (Article 269)

1) Duties in respect of succession to property other than agricultural land.

2) Estate duty in respect of property other than agricultural land.

3) Taxes on railway fares and freights.

4) Taxes other than stamp duties on transactions in stock exchanges and future markets.

5) Taxes on the sale or purchase of goods other than newspapers and on advertisements published therein.

6) Terminal taxes on goods or passengers carried by railway, sea or air.

7) Taxes on the sale or purchase of goods other than newspapers where such sale purchase taxes place in the course of inter-state trade on commerce.

C) Taxes levied and collected by the union but distributed between the union and the states (Article 270).

D) Article 271 specifies surcharge on certain duties and taxes for the purposes of the union.

E) Taxes levied and collected by the union and may be distributed between the union and the states (Article 272).

F) Article 275 provides for the grants-in-aid to be given by the union to the states.

G) Finance Commission (Article 280): Article 280, empowers the president to setup a finance commission within 2 years from the commencement of this constitution and after every fifth year, earlier as he deems necessary. The commission consists of a chairman and four members, appointed by the president. The commission makes recommendations to the president on two specified matters.

i) the distribution between the union and the states of the net proceeds of taxes which are to be or may be divided between them and the allocation between the states of the respective shares of such proceeds.

ii) the principles which should govern the grants in aid of the revenues of the states out of the consolidated fund of India.

and on any other matter referred to the commission by the president in the interests of sound finance.

But the recommendations of the commission are not binding on the centre, the some of the recommendations of source commissions were not accepted by the centre.

H) Article 281 says that the president shall cause every recommendation made by the finance commission under the provisions of this constitution together with an explanatory memorandum as to the action taken thereon to be laid before each house of parliament.

Financially weak position of the states:

Financially states are very weak. Article 274 require, prior recommendation of the president to bills affecting taxation in which states are interested. Article 285 to 288 limit taxation powers of states. The union govt. has the power to borrow money from within and outside the country it has unlimited power of borrowing subject only to such limits fixing parliament under Article 292.

Under Article 293, borrowing powers of the states are limited. Without consent of the centre, states have no power to raise public loan and outside India. Under Article 293 clause 2, the centre may give loans to any state.

The national planning commission plays a decisive role in financial relations under Article 282, it is the planning commission which disburses grants to public purposes.

The states are overburdened with huge expenditure to incur on Salaries, welfare of weaker sections, rural development, irrigation and other areas of development.

Main Recommendations of Sarkaria Commission on Financial Relations :

1. By an amendment to the constitution, the net proceeds of the corporation tax may be shared with the states if parliament by law may provide.
2. Inclusion of corporation tax in the divisible pool, adjustment will have to be carried out by suitably bringing down the shares of states in income tax and union excise duties.
3. In the event of natural calamity, relief must be given to the states. Relief assistance should extend beyond the financial year.
4. The central govt. should give its consent freely to states for borrowing from banks and financial institutions, for period less than one year.
5. Keeping in view the needs of development in the advanced states, a suitable mix of budgetary and non-budgetary access to capital resources may be allowed to them.

Critical Appreciation:

The centre in the legislative field is endowed with the in-built capacity to impose its will on the component units by means of its qualified legal sovereignty. The state legislatures have a very truncated area of authority and even that rump area has been further truncated by virtue of serious inroads where by parliament may make more and more encroachments upon the legislative jurisdiction of the state.

In the administrative field, the centre stands like a colossus. The provision of Article 356 has been much abused and the opposition parties have demanded the deletion of Article 356 from the constitution.

In financial sphere, all important sources of revenues are given in the union list and the position rather so weak that they exist at the doles of the centre.

CASTE IDENTIFICATION IN KARNATAKA: A FOCUS ON THE VVOKKALIGACOMMUNITY

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Introduction

Karnataka, a state located in the southern region of India, is known for its diverse social fabric marked by various linguistic, cultural, and caste groups. The vvokkaligacomunity, historically prominent in Karnataka, has played a significant role in shaping the state's socio-political and economic landscape. This research article delves into the intricacies of caste identification in Karnataka, with a specific focus on the vvokkaligacaste, examining its historical evolution, socio-economic status, and contemporary significance. Another name is calling gowda also

Historical Background of Caste Identification in Karnataka

Caste has been a pivotal aspect of social identity in India, influencing various facets of life, including occupation, social status, and political power. In Karnataka, the caste system has historically been influenced by the migration and settlement of different communities, as well as the impact of ruling dynasties such as the Chalukyas, Hoysalas, gangas and Vijayanagara Empire.

The vokkaligatraditionally identified as an agrarian community, trace their roots to the region's early agrarian societies. They were primarily settled in the southern districts of Karnataka, including Bangalore, Mysore, Mandya, Tumkur, kolara ,chikkaballapura and Hassan. Their economic and social influence grew during the period of the Vijayanagara Empire, where they held significant positions as landholders and warriors.

The vvokkaligaCaste: Origins and Classification

The term "vokkaliga" is derived from the Kannada word "okkal", meaning a cultivator or agriculturist. Another meaning is gowda also known the administrator of village. This etymology highlights their traditional role as farmers, which has long been associated with their identity. The vokkaligacomunity is further divided into sub-groups, such as GangadikaravokkaligaMorasuVokkaligas, Hallikarvokkaliga,kunchitigavvokkaliga, and 52 sub caste , each with distinct cultural practices and traditions.

Caste classification in Karnataka has historically been complex, with multiple overlapping layers defined by region, economic status, and socio-political affiliations. During the colonial period, British administrators conducted surveys and censuses that formalized caste structures, including the identification of vokkaligaas a dominant farming community.

Socio-Economic Position of vokkaliga

The vokkaligacomunity has traditionally occupied a middle-to-upper stratum in the socio-economic hierarchy of Karnataka. As landowners and agriculturalists, they enjoyed significant economic power in rural areas. The Green Revolution further solidified their status as prosperous farmers, enabling them to expand their influence into other economic sectors.

Over time, vokkaligadiversified their economic pursuits, moving beyond agriculture into business, education, and politics. Prominent members of the community have made substantial contributions to

the state's economic development, with many entering professions such as law, engineering, and medicine.

Political Influence of the vokkaligaCaste

The vokkaligahave historically wielded considerable political power in Karnataka. Their influence can be traced back to the formation of the Mysore State and the eventual unification of Karnataka in 1956. The community's political presence became more pronounced in the post-independence era, with leaders such as KengalHanumanthaiah, who played a crucial role in the construction of the VidhanaSoudha, and H.D. Deve Gowda, who served as the Prime Minister of India and continues to be an influential political figure.

The political mobilization of the Vokkaligacommunity has been facilitated by organizations such as the Vokkaligara Sangha,(1904) which was established to promote their welfare and representation. The community's cohesion and strong sense of identity have allowed them to maintain a significant role in state politics, often serving as a counterbalance to other dominant communities such as the Lingayats.

Caste Identification and Reservation Policies

The process of caste identification in Karnataka has been shaped by reservation policies aimed at providing social and educational support to historically disadvantaged communities. The vokkaliga, while classified under the Other Backward Classes (OBC) category in Karnataka, have often found themselves at the center of debates regarding reservation and social justice.

The reservation system, introduced as part of India's affirmative action policies, was designed to address historical injustices and promote the upliftment of marginalized groups. For vokkaliga, their classification under OBC has been both a point of contention and an opportunity for socio-economic advancement. Critics argue that their relatively stronger socio-economic position compared to other OBC communities complicates the question of equitable distribution of resources.

Cultural Identity and Social Practices

The cultural identity of the Vokkaligacommunity is deeply rooted in their agricultural heritage. Festivals such as Sankranti and Ugadi hold special significance, celebrating the harvest season and the renewal of life. Traditional practices include folk dances like Kunitha and cultural rituals that emphasize their connection to the land.

Marriage and kinship practices among vokkaligaoften involve maintaining alliances within the community to preserve their social status and economic interests. This practice has reinforced their cohesion and allowed them to exert collective influence in local and regional matters.

Challenges and Contemporary Issues

Despite their historical advantages, the Vokkaligacommunity faces contemporary challenges, including changing agricultural practices, urbanization, and competition in the political landscape. The decline in agricultural profitability due to fluctuating market conditions and climate change has pushed many younger vokkaligato seek employment in urban areas, leading to shifts in traditional occupations and lifestyles.

In addition, the community's political influence has been met with challenges from emerging groups and movements advocating for broader representation and inclusion. This has led to periodic reassessments of their status within the OBC category and calls for more comprehensive policies to address inequalities across all caste groups in Karnataka.

Conclusion

The Vokkaligacaste's historical roots, socio-economic power, and political influence have made them a key player in Karnataka's social and political landscape. Understanding the nuances of caste identification and the evolution of the Vokkaligacommunity provides valuable insights into broader patterns of social stratification and regional politics in Karnataka. While they have navigated various challenges over time, ongoing developments such as economic shifts, policy changes, and social movements will continue to shape their identity and role in the future.

Efforts to address caste-related disparities must be inclusive and consider the varied socio-economic statuses within each community. The vokkaliga, with their complex history and current standing, exemplify the multifaceted nature of caste dynamics in Karnataka, underscoring the need for policies that promote equitable growth and social harmony.

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2. H. V. Nanjundayya & L. K. AnanthakrishnaIyer (1930) - The Mysore Tribes and Castes, detailing the sub-divisions and cultural practices of the GangadikarVokkaligas.
3. Bhavani Banerjee (1966) - Marriage and Kinship of the GangadikaraVokkaligas of Mysore, focusing on kinship patterns and marriage customs.
4. Mysore Gazetteer (1897) - Provides historical context about caste identities and their administrative significance during the Ganga dynasty era.
5. DevarajUrs' Reforms - Analysis of the rise of OBCs and the "Ahinda" movement's impact on caste politics in Karnataka.
6. Electoral Politics - Studies on how caste affiliations, especially of Vokkaligas, influence Karnataka's political landscape, including the dominance of the JD(S) among Vokkaligas.
7. Historical Role of Vokkaligas - Their contributions as rulers and warriors, especially during the Vijayanagar Empire and later regional power struggles.
8. Sangam Literature - Comparisons between Vokkaligas and other land-owning groups like Vellalas, offering insight into their socio-political roles.
9. The Economic Role of Vokkaligas - Analysis of their prominence as cultivators and landlords in the Old Mysore region.
10. Post-Independence Changes - Exploration of shifts in family structures and rural labor division within the Vvokkaligacommunity.
11. Jajmani System - Insights into traditional caste-based occupational hierarchies and their evolution in Vvokkaligacommunities.
12. Cultural and Religious Practices - Studies on the Vokkaligas' temple traditions and regional customs as part of their identity.
13. Caste Identity in Karnataka Politics - The role of dominant castes, including Vokkaligas, in shaping state politics, especially the interplay between Congress, BJP, and JD(S).

Abstract

Caste plays a pivotal role in shaping the socio-political and cultural landscape of India, with its influence particularly pronounced in Karnataka. This article examines the dynamics of caste identification with a specific focus on the Vokkaligacommunity, a dominant agricultural caste with significant political and social clout in the state. The study explores the historical evolution of the Vokkaligaidentity, tracing its roots to agrarian practices, kinship networks, and regional traditions. It also highlights the community's role in Karnataka's political framework, where Vokkaligaleaders have been instrumental in shaping state policies and governance.

The article further delves into the methods of caste identification, considering how Vokkaliga have maintained their cultural and social cohesion amidst modernization and shifting caste paradigms. Employing a multidisciplinary approach, the research incorporates historical records, ethnographic studies, and contemporary socio-political analysis to provide a nuanced understanding of the community. Key issues addressed include the intersection of caste with economic development, the challenges of caste-based affirmative action, and the community's response to evolving political pressures and identity politics.

By focusing on the Vokkaliga community, the article sheds light on the broader implications of caste identification in Karnataka, offering insights into the persistence of caste as a marker of identity in a rapidly changing socio-economic environment. This study aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse on caste in India, providing a case study of how traditional structures adapt and endure in contemporary society.

AMBEDKAR'S VIEWS ON NATIONALISM- A REVIEW**Dr. Manjunatha R.**

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Abstract

B.R. Ambedkar's notion of nationalism and his understanding of Nationalism is to object internal oppression as well as external domination. He wanted equality and civil rights for those who for centuries deprived of them. Indian society, in view of Ambedkar, was a system which gave no scope for the growth of the sentiment of equality and fraternity which are essential for a democratic form of government. This study attempts to analyze Ambedkar's self generated vision of nationalism and also evaluate Expanding Social Base of Nationalism, Challenge to 'Congress Nationalism', and strengthening nationalism through constitution. According to Ambedkar Nationalism is a dynamic process of social assimilation and therefore nationalism is to receive its perfect harmony in the realization of social brotherhood of men irrespective of caste, colour and creed. Nationalism is not antithetical to humanism or individualism. One can enjoy complete individual freedom within a nationalist framework. Everyone needs a space to think, to grow and liberate. In the present point in time, Nation is the best institution we have to fulfil this purpose. We do need a grand narrative which includes the last woman in the queue. Dr. Ambedkar did give us a grand-narrative of "equality in socio-economic life along with political equality".

Introduction

Over thousands of years, human civilization organized itself first in the form of family, then as religion and today we are organized as nation-state and we live within this institution of nation-state. Foremost of our thoughts and actions, it serves as a center of gravity, obvious at some time and obscure at others. It is one of the most organized, well designed institutions which has an organic relationship with mankind and where universal ideas like freedom, equality and democracy have a good chance to flourish.

The Bhartiya concept of Rashtra could be considered a parallel to the western term 'Nation' but both are also different on several counts. The primary difference between the two stems from the fact that Rashtra is more of an ethic-spiritual concept while Nation is a cultural concept.

Many Indian leaders like Sri Arvindo, Gandhi, Nehru, Tilak, Tagore and DeenDayalUpadhyay delved into the idea of Indian nation and nationalism. Their ideas are either spiritual, meta-physical or statistics. In this paper it is tried to trace Dr. BhimRaoAmbedkar's ideas and reflections on Nationalism. Over the years, ideas of Ambedkar have become stronger and more relevant to the contemporary discourse.

Ambedkar's views on Nationalism

Dr. BhimraoRamjiAmbedkar (1891-1956), the great Indian Constitution maker and 'a symbol of revolt'(as mentioned by Jawaharlal Nehru, The first Prime Minister of India), was one of the leading nation-builders of modern India. The reactions of Dalits (untouchables) to the criticism on Ambedkar's role in the freedom struggle of India and its construction of the national movement have led to a reconsideration of his views or ideas on nationalism. Ambedkar's thought in general and nationalism in particular is not merely ideas or opinions of a great thinker. These are aspects of a collective ideology which are operating as a motor force, in struggle with other ideologies in the fast changing society. Of all the modern Indian ideologies, it is Ambedkar who alone attempted to elaborate a full-fledged theory

of nationalism and sought to apply it critically to the Indian situation. But, it is a pity that theoretical reflections and justifications were virtually on-existent within the nationalist movement in India. One section asserted that India as Hindu has been eternal and the Indian nation is waking up from its long stupor, imposed on it by its external enemies, other section treated it the phase 'nation-in-the making' whenever difficulties arose. As against this, Ambedkar grappled with this ideology of nineteenth century Europe, deconstructed it as to what is perennial and peripheral in it and showed how it could be critically applied to the peculiarities of the colonial Indian situation.

Nationalism in Ambedkar initiated to object internal oppression as well as external domination. He wanted equality and civil rights for those who for centuries deprived of them. Indian society, in view of Ambedkar, was a system which gave no scope for the growth of the sentiment of equality and fraternity which are essential for a democratic form of government. Many people were deprived of the basic human rights. He wanted constitutional safeguards to protect oppressed. Ambedkar was of the outlook that Indian society was nothing but gradation of caste which consists of ascending scale of reverence and descending scale of contempt. Ambedkar's view was very transparent regarding foreign domination. Ambedkar viewed that in spite of realizing the necessity of removing some social evils which had horrified the lives of down-trodden people, British attitude was indifferent in eradicating some social evils simply because of the reason that its intervention in the-then existing code of social and economic life would give rise to resistance.

Ambedkar's spirit of nationalism took a proper shape through the struggle against such British rule although foreign rule had been the potential force in the country like India. Nationalism in Ambedkar stems from his spirit of dignity both for the people and for the country. He had profound feeling for the poor and untouchables which induced him to fight against denial of basic human rights. Such attitudes of Ambedkar were called by some congress leader as anti-national, but in true sense, it was nothing but expression of humanism and nationalism to which he sincerely devoted himself.

Ambedkar elaborated on the idea of Nationality and Nationalism in his book *Pakistan or the Partition of India*. He describes nationality as a, "consciousness of kind, awareness of the existence of that tie of kinship" and nationalism as "the desire for a separate national existence for those who are bound by this tie of kinship." It is true that there cannot be nationalism without the feeling of nationality. But, it is important to bear in mind that the converse is not always true. The feeling of nationality may be present and yet the feeling of nationalism may be quite absent. That is to say, nationality does not in all cases produce nationalism. For nationality to flame into nationalism two conditions must exist. First, there must arise the will to live as a nation. Nationalism is the dynamic expression of that desire. Secondly, there must be a territory which nationalism could occupy and make it a state, as well as a cultural home of the nation. Without such a territory, nationalism, to use Lord Acton's phrase, would be a soul as it were wandering in search of a body in which to begin life over again and dies out finding none.

Expanding Social Base of Nationalism

Ambedkar had immense faith in the bright future and evolution of this country. Even when he spoke of attaining freedom for India, his ultimate goal was to unite the people. He said, "So far as the ultimate goal is concerned, none of us have any apprehension or doubt. Our difficulty was not about the ultimate thing but how to unite the heterogeneous mass that we are today to take a decision in common and march in a cooperative way on that road, which is bound to lead us to unity."

Ambedkar clearly spoke in a felicitation program of his 55th birth anniversary, "I have loyalty to our people inhabiting this country. I have also loyalty to this country. I have no doubt that you have the

same. All of us want this country to be free. So far as I am concerned my conduct has been guided by the consideration that we shall place no great difficulties in the way of this country achieving its freedom.”

Ambedkar was not against the idea of nationalism but against the Congress’s version which entailed freedom of India from British colonialism but not from Brahminical imperialism under which millions of Scheduled Castes had been yoked for hundreds of years. It was Ambedkar’s political challenge which compelled the Congress to appreciate the national significance of the problem of castes and to adopt measures which significantly contributed towards broadening and strengthening the social base of Indian nationalism.

Ambedkar’s Challenge to ‘Congress Nationalism’

Indian nationalism in its initial stages, by the very nature of its historical development, was an upper class (upper castes) phenomenon, reflecting the interests and aspirations of its members. Naturally when nationalists spoke in terms of national interest they certainly meant their own (class) interests. The evocation of ‘nation’ was a necessary ritual to ensure the much needed popular support for an essentially partisan cause. This sectarian approach to nationalism could be seen in the writings of none other than Pt. Nehru who later singled out as an example of a ‘left liberal’ view. He writes in his seminal work *Discovery of India* that mixture of religion and philosophy, history and tradition, custom and social structure, which in its wide fold included almost every aspect of the life of India, and which might be called Brahminism or (to use a later word) Hinduism, became the symbol of nationalism. It was indeed a national religion.

The sectarian character of Indian nationalism persisted even after the nascent upper castes’ movement developed into a truly mass-supported anti-imperialist national liberation movement enlisting the support of millions of people cutting across the traditional social divisions. And, it is this failure to change its basically pro-upper class/castes orientation despite a basic shift in its underlying social base that Indian national movement in due course helped the rise of new sectarian socio-political currents, running parallel to the mainstream national movement. Ambedkar’s emergence on the Indian political scene in 1920s, commencing the advent of Dalit (the scheduled castes) politics, was simply the manifestation of the same process.

Ambedkar’s Dalit politics posed no really significant threat to the overall domination of the traditional ruling class, yet it certainly exposed the hollowness of the Congress’s nationalist claim to represent the whole nation. Finally, the unwillingness of the nationalist leadership to attack the long unresolved social contradictions at the base of the Hindu social order propelled people like Ambedkar to contest the claim of the Indian National Congress to represent the scheduled castes.

It was in the backdrop of this escapist attitude of the Congress brand of nationalism that an alternative subaltern nationalism was born through Ambedkar. Ambedkar took up this question from social below and elevated it to a political high by linking this social question of caste with the political question of democracy and nationalism. Such an effort to prioritize society over polity and then linking them together was unprecedented in India before Ambedkar. Gandhi can be said to have made such an effort but his approach was obscure and primitive. According to Ambedkar,

“Without social union, political unity is difficult to be achieved. If achieved, it would be as precarious as a summer sapling, liable to be uprooted by the gust of a hostile wind. With mere political unity, India may be a State. But to be a State is not to be a nation and a State, which is not a nation, has small prospects of survival in the struggle for existence.”

Strengthening Nationalism through Constitution

Ambedkar opposed insertion of Article 370 which gives special status to the state of Jammu & Kashmir but Nehru still went ahead with it to appease Sheikh Abdullah. Ambedkar wrote to Sheikh Abdullah on Article 370, "You wish India should protect your borders, she should build roads in your area, she should supply you food grains, and Kashmir should get equal status as India. But Government of India should have only limited powers and Indian people should have no rights in Kashmir. To give consent to this proposal would be a treacherous thing against the Interest of India and I, as the Law Minister of India, will never do it."

Justice K. Ramaswamy while probing into the legal aspects of nationalism likes to call Ambedkar a true democrat, a nationalist to the core and a patriot of highest order on various grounds. He was the author and principal actor to make the 'Directive Principles' as part of the constitutional scheme. When it was criticized that the directive principles could not be enforced in a court of law, Ambedkar answered that though they were not enforceable, the succeeding majority political party in Parliament or Legislative Assembly would be bound by them as an inbuilt part of their economic program in the governance, despite their policy in its manifesto and are bound by the Constitution. Ambedkar, in his Constitutional schema of nationalism, undertook the task of strengthening the Executive in particular and the notion of 'Integrated Bharat' in general.

Rising above the regional, linguistic and communal barriers in a true republican spirit, Ambedkar invented a democratic nationalism consisting of Uniform Civil Code for India. His views of Uniform Civil Code were radically different from his contemporaries including Nehru who in principles accepted Hindu Code Bill and Uniform Civil Code but in practice, failed to get the Bill passed in one go, in spite of being in Government with majority. Ambedkar on the other hand made it a point to add the word 'fraternity' in the Preamble to the Constitution in order to inculcate the sense of common brotherhood of all Indians, of Indians being one people; it is the principle which gives unity and solidarity to social life.

He was also critical of Muslim Personal Law and tried his best to abolish it in favour of Uniform Civil Code. Ambedkar did not agree to the fact that Muslims had any immutable and uniform laws in India up to 1935. Ambedkar emphasized that in a secular state religion should not be allowed to govern all human activities and that Personal Laws should be divorced from religion.

Dr. Ambedkar in his very first speech in the Constituent Assembly on 17 December 1946 had emphasized the need to create a strong Centre in order to ensure that India's freedom was not jeopardized as had happened in the past on account of a weak central administration. His view was hailed by the Assembly and came later to be reflected in the Emergency Provisions of the Constitution. Undoubtedly the states are sovereign in normal times but by virtue of these provisions, the Centre becomes all-powerful and assumes control over all affairs of the nation whenever a situation arises which poses a danger to the security of the state.

Conclusion

There is no doubt that Ambedkar was vehemently opposed to the unjust social stratification in India, but to say that he was against the nation is wholly wrong. He was definitely against the Congress version of Nationalism. Ambedkar says, "I know my position has not been understood properly in the country. I say that whenever there has been a conflict between my personal interests of the country as a whole, I have always placed the claims of the country above my personal claims. I have never pursued the path of private gain... so far as the demands of the country are concerned, I have never lagged behind".

It is evident from the above discussion that Ambedkar was a national leader who understood the problems of the most exploited communities and tried to bring them into the main stream. He expanded the social base of Indian nationalism which helped first to attain freedom and later to put the country

on path of progress. Today, when all thought converges around inclusive politics, Ambedkar has become more relevant than ever.

Nationalism is a dynamic process of social assimilation and therefore nationalism is to receive its perfect harmony in the realization of social brotherhood of men irrespective of caste, colour and creed. Nationalism is not antithetical to humanism or individualism. One can enjoy complete individual freedom within a nationalist framework. Everyone needs a space to think, to grow and liberate. In the present point in time, Nation is the best institution we have to fulfil this purpose. We do need a grand narrative which includes the last woman in the queue. Dr. Ambedkar did give us a grand-narrative of “equality in socio-economic life along with political equality”.

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THE ROLE OF FEDERALISM IN SHAPING INDIA'S DEMOCRATIC IDENTITY: A STUDY OF PLURALISM AND POLITICAL DISCOURSE

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Abstract

India, a vast and diverse nation, presents a unique case of federalism where regional identities and political autonomy coalesce with the central authority of the Union. This paper examines the role of federalism in shaping India's democratic identity, with an emphasis on pluralism and political discourse. It argues that India's federal structure not only accommodates the country's vast ethnic, linguistic, and cultural diversities but also enables a broader political dialogue, fostering an inclusive national identity. The paper analyzes how the federal framework contributes to the protection of regional autonomy while simultaneously promoting a unified democratic framework at the national level.

Introduction:

India's federal system is a defining feature of its democracy. Unlike many federal systems around the world, India's unique blend of regional autonomy and central authority plays a critical role in maintaining national cohesion while respecting regional diversity. The Indian Constitution, adopted in 1950, provides a framework for balancing the powers between the central government and the states. However, the relationship between these two levels of governance is constantly shaped by evolving political and social dynamics, particularly the politics of identity. This paper delves into the role federalism plays in reinforcing India's pluralistic democracy and shaping political discourse, and it explores how federalism accommodates diverse regional demands without undermining the democratic fabric of the nation.

Literature Review:

1. **Kohli, A. (1990).** Democracy and Discontent: India's Growing Crisis of Governability. Cambridge University Press.
Kohli's work addresses how federalism in India manages the challenges posed by regional aspirations, particularly the tensions between regional identity politics and the need for national integration.
2. **Brass, P. R. (1991).** Ethnicity and Nationalism: Theory and Comparison. Sage Publications.
Brass analyzes the role of ethnicity and regionalism in shaping the political landscape of India, highlighting how federalism accommodates these forces within a democratic framework.
3. **Chhibber, P., & Verma, R. (2018).** Indian Politics in Comparative Perspective. Cambridge University Press.
Chhibber and Verma explore how India's political system, with its unique brand of federalism, supports pluralism and the accommodation of diverse political discourses in a democracy.

Objectives:

1. **To analyze the role of federalism in shaping India's democratic identity:** The paper will explore how India's federal structure has influenced its democratic principles, particularly in terms of accommodating diverse identities.
2. **To understand how pluralism within federalism impacts political discourse:** The study aims to explore how pluralism, a characteristic feature of India's federal system, affects the nature of political discourse across the country.
3. **To assess the challenges and benefits of India's federal system in maintaining political stability:** The research will analyze how India's unique federal structure helps in maintaining political stability while respecting regional aspirations and demands..

Methodology:

This research article adopts a secondary data-based methodology, relying on previously collected data and literature for analysis. The approach includes the following steps:

- Literature Review: Analysis of academic journals, books, and government reports on Indian federalism and pluralism.
- Political Studies: Review of existing studies on state-central relations and political movements.
- Government Reports: Examination of constitutional documents and policy reports related to federalism.
- Discussions: Insights from scholars and political analysts on federalism's impact on democracy.

Findings and Analysis:**1. Federalism and India's Democratic Identity**

Federalism in India is not merely a constitutional structure but a dynamic system that plays an instrumental role in shaping the country's democratic identity. India is a multi-lingual, multi-religious, and multi-ethnic society, and the federal system allows for the expression of this diversity within the political framework of the state. By providing a space for regional political participation, the federal structure serves as a mechanism for accommodating regional aspirations and ethnic identities. In this respect, federalism is not just a division of power; it is a process through which Indian democracy manifests its pluralism.

2. Pluralism in the Indian Federal Framework

Pluralism, in the context of India's federalism, refers to the recognition and accommodation of various social, cultural, and political identities. The Indian federal system is designed to allow regions to express their distinct identities through political representation and autonomy. For instance, states like Tamil Nadu, Punjab, and West Bengal have historically leveraged their regional identities to influence national politics. This pluralism within the federal structure facilitates the recognition of diverse cultures, languages, and political ideologies, thereby fostering a broader, more inclusive democratic discourse.

3. Political Discourse and Federalism

India's political discourse has been profoundly shaped by its federal structure. Political debates in the country are often framed by the interests and ideologies of different states, with regional parties playing a significant role in the national discourse. The federal system gives these regional parties a platform to influence national policies, which is evident in the way state elections are intertwined with national politics. In this sense, federalism does not just divide power but also facilitates the diversity of political ideas and movements, shaping national policy and governance.

For example, the language issue in India has been a prominent topic of political discourse. The demands for official status for regional languages, such as Tamil or Bengali, often result in debates that reflect both regional pride and the need for a common national identity. Similarly, issues related to religion, caste, and economic development are often discussed through the lens of regional politics, which makes federalism an important space for public deliberation.

4. Federalism and Political Stability

Despite the challenges posed by identity-based politics, federalism in India has, to a large extent, contributed to political stability. The federal structure accommodates the aspirations of regional political entities while maintaining national integrity. One of the most significant features of Indian federalism is the distribution of powers in the Constitution, which allows states a degree of autonomy, particularly in matters concerning local governance, education, health, and cultural preservation. However, this autonomy is balanced by the strong central authority that ensures the protection of national interests. This balance helps mitigate regional tensions and ensures that the unity of the nation is preserved, even as regional demands are addressed.

5. Challenges to Federalism in India

While federalism has been a cornerstone of India's democracy, it is not without challenges. The growing demands for greater autonomy, especially from smaller states and regional parties, often lead to tensions with the central government. The rise of identity politics, especially in the context of linguistic, ethnic, and religious differences, sometimes leads to separatist tendencies or calls for autonomy that threaten the unity of the nation. The case of Jammu and Kashmir, for instance, illustrates the complexities of balancing regional autonomy with national cohesion in a democratic system.

Another challenge lies in the uneven development across states, which sometimes exacerbates regional inequalities and fuels discontent. This has led to demands for a more decentralized federal system that could address regional disparities more effectively. The central government's reluctance to grant more autonomy to certain states, such as the demand for a separate state in Telangana or the calls for autonomy in Nagaland and Kashmir, highlights the continuing tension between federal autonomy and central control.

Conclusion

India's federalism plays a crucial role in shaping its democratic identity by accommodating the pluralistic nature of its society. While the federal structure provides a framework for managing regional diversity, it also enables a broader political discourse, where the diversity of identities and interests can be expressed within a democratic setting. The delicate balancing act between regional autonomy and national unity has allowed India to maintain political stability while preserving its rich cultural and linguistic diversity. However, as India continues to evolve, the challenges of balancing federalism, regional demands, and national cohesion remain central to its democratic future.

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IMPACT OF NATIONAL DEMOCRATIC ALLIANCE'S POLITICAL IDEOLOGY ON DEMOCRACY SOME ISSUES AND CONCERNS IN INDIA

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Abstract

India is a largest liberal democratic nation in the world .Its polity is edifies on largest written constitution. This democratic constitution is accommodative of diversity. people are cherishing multiplicity of values, ethos and practices inherent in their religion and culture. India's democratic polity cannot be insulated from its religion, culture, caste and communities. Various political parties are thriving and competing for power. They have been championing their own ideologies suitable to their party identities and political conveniences. congress (I) led UPA coalitions and BJP led NDA coalition have also been articulating their own ideologies to win over people to their sides for power formation, power retention, power consolidation and power management. However, this paper attempts to examine the impact of Bharatiya Janata Party led National Democratic Alliance's ideology on democracy in India .Simultaneously, it uncovers some issues and concerns which are gripping the imagination of people in the ebb and flow of India's democratic party politics. Paper concludes with the observation that although BJP led NDA's ideology is quite often met with political resistance it is contributing to the transformation of India nationally and globally.

Key Words

1. NDA – National Democratic Alliance
 2. BJP – BharathiyaJanatha Party
-

Introduction

Contemporary politics in India is replied with wide variety of issues and concerns political parties, coalition politics, party governments, collation Government and political ideology are predominant among them India's liberal multi party democracy is a broader platform for definitive articulation of diverse ideologist for the mobilization and counter mobilisation of various section of the electorate for the explanation of socio economic support base and also for the consolidation of votes during elections.

Inconsequence India's competitive power politics is becoming intense. The entire gamut of political process is experiencing more heat than light BJP lead NDA's political ideology in particularly appears to be a hard nuts to crack for some. Therefore it's impact on democracy and issues and concerns springing from it are gravitating attention for penetrative probe.

Moreover BJP the incarnation of Bharatiya Jana Sangha has approximately 45 years of history. It formed National democratic aliens on 15th may 1998. NDA's during 27 years of its existence has been thriving leaps and bounds. Now under them prime minister ship of Narendra Modi and his supreme leadership BJP lead NDA's is becoming more and more influential despite penchant opposition from Central leftist and left of centre political parties.

Now it is ruling alliance not only at the union level but also in 19 states and one union territory. Hence impact of its political ideology on democracy in India is not only notable but worthy of rumination.

Therefore this research paper attempts to examine impact of national democratic alliance ideology on democracy in India and focuses on some issues and concerns which are hotly debated in contemporary Indian politics.

Conceptualization

Terms like ideology, political party coalition government, BJP and NDA are frequently used in this paper. For precise understanding of their definitions are very much necessary.

Political party

“Political party is an organised body with voluntary membership. Its concerted energy is employed in the pursuit of political power.”¹

“ A political party is a community of individual linked together by common objectives and guided by the desire to achieve power or influence power within a political system.”²

A party is a group whose members purpose to act in concert in the competitive struggle for political power.”³

Hands political parties that a part and partial of the government. It will wait for the power and as soon as it got its will form a new government. If any party fail to got the majority two or more parties jointly form a new government it is called coalition politics.

Coalition government

Amitabh Mattu describes (in his book collision politics in India problems and prospects) as coalition politics as a system where political alliances are formed when no single party can secure a majority required ring compromised and accommodation among diverse political entities to achieve a common minimum program.

According to SanjayaBaru coalition politics as a reflection of India's diversity were regional parties play a pivotal role in shaping national policy often leading to a balancing act between regional and Central priorities (India's power elite class cast and cultural revolution).

Hence coalition party is the mutual understanding between the political parties to form the government.

The political parties are formed on the basis of a kind of interest and it has ideology too.

Ideology

“Ideologies are defined as a set of believes values and ideas that justify and maintain the interest of a particular class or social group particularly the ruling class”⁴.

Ideology is a set of ideas and beliefs that inspires political moments and actions⁵.

Hence ideology is political parties will rule the nation if they will assume power if political parties fail to follow their ideology they will lose their political power and faith of the people as well.

What is BJP then?

BJP is not only the national party but also it is one of the strong parties of India. And it formed 6th April 1980 by Atal Bihari Vajpayee, L K Advani ever since it's inception it's objective has been to give political representation to Hindu activist and it is formed on the ideology of Hindutva as well.

in 1996loksabha election BJP had alone won 161 seats a its alliance won 33 seats. Although it was give opportunity to form the government on the basis seats it won on the condition that it was to prove majority in loksabha but unfortunately AB Vajpayee was unable to mobilize the required number of seats. He failed to prove majority therefore his 13 day government was literally pulled down in. No confidence motion moved by Sri.Sitaram kesari the then President of Indian National Congress on 26 may 1996.the non BJP led alliance political parties.BJP failed to prove majority in loksabha subsequently AB Vajpayee had tendered his resignation to the prime minister ship.

Now BJP led NDA coalition government is the government of 41 political parties at the centre.

Similarly National Democratic alliance it is the alliance is formed in 1996 under the party leadership of Bharatiya Janata Party. Now this alliance has 41 political parties.

Impact of BJP led NDAs ideology on Indian democracy .

Bharatiya Janata party is the corner stone of national democratic alliance.

Though NDA's government is coalition of 41 political parties it is primarily led by BJP hence bjps ideology is a cohesive force for NDA as well.

1. Hindutva Ideology

BJP party is formed on the basis of the concept of Hindutva. It is created because to give political representation to Hindu activists. This concept is popularised by VinayakaDamodarSavarkar. He Argue that India is the nation for traditional Hindus according to him formerly India is the nation of Hindus who lived and living in India.

Issues :

Concept of Hindutva is creating the polarization in India and it marginalised the minority groups such as Muslims Christians. For example citizenship amendment act, it excludes the Muslims. The concept of Hindutva ideology questions the concept of secularism. India is a democratic country that values all the religions and give equal representation to all the religions along with the people of India. The concept of Hindutva ideology is one not the secular concept but it differentiate between religions.

Concerns :

The concern of the ideology Hindutva is the representation of the tradition of India and it is the identity of natives of India as well. It is protecting the culture and rich heritage of our country.

It showcases the rich history of our culture to the world through the concept of Hindutva .

2. Strong central government.

India is the nation which exercises decentralisation of power. Decentralization of power is nothing but the distribution of power between centre and state. According to NDA's government strong central government is the basis for the development of the nation.

Issues:

The concept of centralisation is questions the concept of federalism in India federal system means the distribution of power to state as well as the centre but centralisation focuses on giving the power to the centre. it curtail the power of States.

Concerns:

Though we have a federal system, we can see the unitary biased system.. in judiciary election , decides border issues of the states renamed the states names etc.

Here centralisation represents unity of the nation. Through centralisation of powers the decision regarding nation can take early as possible without wasting time. It has concern over state powers also but to create oneness among nation it can be practiced.

3. Universal economic policies:

The NDA's government is implemented various economic policies that is all over India. Through GST, and other economic policies.

Issues :

Without social concern and proper policies GST and other economic policies are creating economic pressure over the people that to the people who are working on the street is suffering a lot. It is also leads to social stress and other things.

Concerns :

The concept of universal economic policies are brought in India to create equal economic stability along with curtailing of corruption. And make in India is one of the concerns which promote home goods and it develops the home made products. It will encourage the new era in the business sector etc .

Conclusion :

Apart from these NDA's ideologies there are other issues and concerns also there like article 370 about triple Talaq about universal education system national education policy propaganda NDA's media rights, and the construction of Ram Mandir etc. the concern of NDA's governments is social in nature and it represents some of the key ideologies that represents social harmony equal distribution of wealth. But the core ideology of NDA's government is that to make the nation as globally developed nation. Make in India is the example for the economic development of the nation as well. Of course it has its own challenges too. It may not look university in nature for other ideological perspective but it also trying its best to do. In short, BJP led NDA government aims at consolidating space for muscular nationalism for national security and economic nationalism for transforming India into a self reliant and self confident developed nation. It is also seeking to invigorate cultural and religious nationalism in order to revive and rever age old principles of Hinduism and Hindu religion. It is trying to broaden deepen stretch and diversify it's support base on the basis of its ideology characterised by its abiding faith in Hindu majoritarianism, constitutionalism neo liberalism, globalism and above all vasudaiva kutumbakam which it self is the crux of cosmopolitanism.

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CULTURAL DIVERSITY AND NATIONAL UNITY**Chanabasppa Prabhakar**

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Abstract

India is a multi-ethnic and culturally diverse society that has witnessed conflicts arising from this ethnic and cultural diversity. This paper expounds such conceptual issues as ethnicity, cultural diversity and national integration. It is argued that national integration in the Indian context has been an attempt to establish "unity in diversity", seeking to wish away socio-cultural differences and imposing uniformity in spite of complex cultural diversity. This has created more conflict and posed obstacles to unity, peaceful coexistence, progress and stable development. It recommends that national integration and its benefits can be realized only with the development and entrenchment of a supportive public culture; understanding, respecting and tolerating differences occasioned by socio-cultural diversity; as well as the development of new institutions and mechanisms that address poverty, revenue allocation and other national issues peacefully.

Keywords: Social, Cultural Diversity, National Integration, Assimilation

Introduction

India is a land of 130 Crore people, an 8000-year old history, speaking 450 different languages, celebrating 100 different festivals across 28 different states with their unique clothing, cuisine, and creative arts that change every few kilometers. This unique diversity makes India. Indian culture is one of the most ancient cultures present in the world. The country is quite diverse and is home to several communities, each of which has its own culture and traditions. It is this combination of various splendid cultures that make India one of a kind.

The Diversity celebration is becoming an integral part of a multi-cultural, multi-religious and multi-lingual country like India. Celebrating diversity supports and enhances where diverse perspectives, cultures and values are accepted, appreciated and celebrated. Diversity is the sum total of colour, religion and creed, sexual orientation, age and ability. The recognition of a common humanity is the first step in the celebration of differences – differences that inform cultures, values, minds, and all ways of being in the world. Diversity is the chief element of the creative life force.

Diversity in India

India is a plural society both in letter and spirit. It is rightly characterized by its unity and diversity. A grand synthesis of cultures, religions and languages of the people belonging to different castes and communities has upheld its unity and cohesiveness despite multiple foreign invasions. National unity and integrity have been maintained even through sharp economic and social inequalities have obstructed the emergence of egalitarian social relations. It is this synthesis which has made India a unique behind of cultures.

The term 'diversity' emphasizes differences rather than inequalities. Diversity means variety of races, religions, languages, castes and cultures. Unity means integration. It is a social psychological condition. It connotes a sense of oneness. It stands for the bonds, which hold the members of a society together.

Unity in diversity essentially means "unity without uniformity" and "diversity without fragmentation". It is based on the notion that diversity enriches human interaction. When we say that India is a nation of great cultural diversity, we mean that there are many different types of social groups

and communities living here. These are communities defined by cultural markers such as language, religion, sect, race, or caste.

Forms of diversity in India

❖ Religious diversity

India is a land of multiple religions. Apart from the tribal societies, many of whom still live in the pre-religious state of animism and magic, the Indian population consists of the Hindus (82.41%), Muslims (11.6%), Christians (2.32%), Sikhs (1.99%), Buddhists (0.77%) and Jains (0.41%). The Hindus themselves are divided into several sects such as Vaishnavas, Shaivates, Shaktas, Smartas etc. Similarly, the Muslims are divided into sects such as Shias, Sunnis, Ahmadiyas etc.

❖ Linguistic diversity

Languages spoken in India belong to several language families, the major ones being the Indo-Aryan languages spoken by 75 Indians and the Dravidian languages spoken by 20% of Indians. Other languages belong to the Austroasiatic, Sino-Tibetan, Tai-Kadai, and a few other minor language families and isolates, India has the world's second highest number of languages, after Papua New Guinea.

❖ Racial diversity

1931 census classified India's racial diversity in the following groups- The Negrito, The Proto-Australoid, The Mongoloid, The Mediterranean, The Western Brachycephals and the Nordic. Representatives of all the three major races of the world, namely Caucasoid, Mongoloid, and Negroid, are found in India.

❖ Caste diversity

The term caste has been used to refer to both varna as well as jati. Varna is the four-fold division of society according to functional differentiation. Thus, the four varnas include Brahmins, Kshatriyas, Vaishyas and Shudras and an outcaste group whereas Jati refers to a hereditary endogamous status group practicing a specific traditional occupation.. There are more than 3000 jatis and there is no All India system of ranking them in order and status. The jati system is not static and there is mobility in the system, through which jatis have changed their position over years.

❖ Cultural diversity

Cultural patterns reflect regional variations. Because of population diversity, there is immense variety in Indian culture as it is a blend of various cultures. Different religion, castes, and regions follow their own tradition and culture. Thus, there is variation in art, architecture, dance forms, theatre forms, and music.

❖ Geographical diversity

Spanning across an area of 3.28 million square kilometre, India is a vast country with a diversity of physical features like dry deserts, evergreen forests, lofty mountains, perennial and non-perennial river systems, long coasts and fertile plains.

What are the uses of celebrating diversity?

By celebrating diversity a society is exposed to certain facts which never crossed the minds in a closeted society dominated by unilateral thinking and appreciation of life around.

- Knowledge is the key to tolerance
- To gain a new perspective on the lives of others around you as well as around the world.
- Cultural celebrations foster respect and open-mindedness for other cultures
- Celebrating differences, as well as common interests, helps unite and educate

- To understand others' perspectives, to broaden our own, and to fully experience and educate oneself
- It promotes tolerance and understanding between different cultures
- It enriches our community through shared experiences with different people;
- Through each other's diversity, we become more aware of our own.
- Understanding people and their backgrounds are crucial to personal and community growth
- It makes us think of other people around us with different perspectives and viewpoints
- It helps to relate to and understand those with different social, economic, and educational backgrounds

In 2001, UNESCO declared 21 May as UN World Day for Cultural Diversity for Dialogue and Development. It's a chance to celebrate the cultural diversity of people around us and find out more about what we have in common, rather than what separates us.

Ways to celebrate diversity

1. Visit an exhibition or a museum dedicated to other cultures

A visit to a local museum or exhibition may inspire to create something yourself, and heighten desire to learn about a new culture. A major point of disagreement between different cultures is lack of understanding of each other's cultures. In the absence of proper understanding, mutual distrust and one-sided views further alienate the hearts and minds of the people.

2. Learn about other religions

Dalai Lama wrote 'Finding common ground among faiths can help us bridge needless divides, at a time when unified action is more crucial than ever.' Religious clashes and conflicts are more because people object to or criticize other religion without fully being aware of it. The prejudice on the part of all, makes celebrating diversity not only difficult but also complicated. Understanding each other in full is key to celebrating diversity.

3. Movie and music

Watching movies and listening to music from across borders be it within India or around would broaden the scope of understanding better. It is well known that hit movies in any regional language or a Hindi movie is dubbed into different languages help to celebrate diversity. Because, the key theme of the movie is made to reach all Indians. The Roja movie, made in the background of inter-community relationships, gained a national appreciation and made people understand that it is very important to be human than something else.

In India, classical music has come from different parts of India with distinct styles, flair, and purity. Hindustani classical music is as good as Carnatic music for a lover of music irrespective of creed, colour, and religion. The legends of Indian musicians who made Indian music popular across the world include Allah Rakha, Bismillah Khan, Balamurali Krishna, MS Subbalakshmi, Honnappa Bhagavathar, Shiva Kumar Sharma, Hari Prasad Chaurasia, and many others. The language of music is peace, inner harmony, and pleasure.

4. Exchange of food

Food all over the world unites people like no other connection. Food is cultural because the same food is not cooked all over the world. Therefore, attempting to know and taste different food leads one to get into a new culture and discover it. This not only enriches our knowledge but also drives away any misconceptions we had about a culture.

5. Traditional stories from other cultures

Reading and learning about stories from another culture is a great way to expand our knowledge of the world. Many traditional folk tales have universal themes. Each of the Indian states has a treasure house of values and morals expressed in terms of culture. The exchange of stories, rooted in different cultures, is in fact an exchange of higher values of other cultures.

6. Learning languages

Language and culture are inseparable. India is a land of huge diversity. What is practiced in the North, South, East, and Western regions of India will differ substantially. Many times, two neighbouring states may not know the opposite languages. The practice of many languages gives a cosmopolitan colour to a state in India. For instance, in Karnataka, particularly in Bangalore at least 4-5 languages are spoken by the people. Cultural celebrations foster respect and open-mindedness for other cultures. Celebrating our differences, as well as our common interests, helps unite and educate us.

Factors Leading to Unity and Diversity in India

1. Constitutional identity

The entire country is governed by single constitution. Most of the states follow a generalised scheme of 3-tier government structure, thus imparting uniformity in national governance framework. Further, the constitution guarantees certain fundamental rights to all citizens regardless of their age, gender, class, caste, religion, etc.

2. Religious co-existence

Religion tolerance is the unique feature of religions in India due to which multiple religions co-exist. Freedom of religion in India is guaranteed by the Constitution. More religion and no state religion and all religions are given equal preference there in the state.

3. Inter-State mobility

The Constitution guarantees freedom to move throughout the territory of India under Article 19, thus promoting a sense of unity. Other factors such as uniform pattern of law, penal code, and administration (All India Services) too lead to uniformity in the criminal justice system and policy implementation.

4. Economic integration

The Constitution secures the freedom of Trade, Commerce and Intercourse within the Territory of India. Further, the Goods and Service Tax (GST) have paved way for 'one country, one tax, one national market', thus facilitating unity among different regions.

5. Institution of pilgrimage and religious practices

In India, religion and spirituality have great significance. Religious shrines and holy rivers are spread throughout the length and breadth of the country and closely related to them is the age-old culture of pilgrimage, which has always moved people to various parts of the country and fostered in them a sense of geo-cultural unity.

6. Fairs and festivals

They also act as integrating factors as people from all parts of the country celebrate them as per their own local traditions. For instance, Diwali is celebrated by Hindus; Eid and Christmas are celebrated by Muslims and Christians respectively. Celebration of inter-religious festivals is also seen in India.

Conclusion:

The cultural, linguistic, and religious diversity in India is a testament to the rich cultural heritage of the country. The diversity has a profound impact on the social fabric of the country and shapes its

national identity, creating a unique and vibrant society. Cultural diversity helps promote peaceful coexistence among people from different cultures and ethnic backgrounds in their workplace, institutions, and social settings. Cultural diversity helps people to acknowledge that the world comprises different types of people from different cultural settings. The cultural, linguistic, and religious diversity in India is a testament to the rich cultural heritage of the country. The diversity has a profound impact on the social fabric of the country and shapes its national identity, creating a unique and vibrant society.

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FEDERALISM IN INDIA- AN ASSESSMENT OF THE CENTRE- STATE RELATIONS IN THE PRESENT SCENARIO

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Abstract

Federalism is a system of governance where power is shared between a central authority and regional or state governments. This structure allows both levels of government to control specific areas, promoting a balance between regional autonomy and national unity. In India, federalism is defined by the Constitution, which divides powers between the central government and the states. While this arrangement ensures autonomy for states in certain matters, it also upholds a strong central government to maintain unity. Over time, Centre-State relations have evolved, shaped by constitutional provisions, political developments, and socio-economic factors. The Indian Constitution establishes a federal framework with a dominant central government and considerable state autonomy. However, recent trends have seen the central government assert greater control over areas traditionally managed by the states. For instance, the implementation of the Goods and Services Tax (GST) streamlined taxation, but some states have raised concerns about revenue loss and reduced fiscal autonomy. Additionally, the centralization of administrative power, especially in sectors like security, health, and education, has sparked debates about the erosion of states' rights to make independent decisions. The rise of coalition politics and the influence of national parties in state elections have further shifted the balance of power, often concentrating authority at the Centre and limiting states' decision-making abilities. Despite these challenges, India's federal structure remains adaptable, facilitating both cooperation and conflict. There is a growing need for a more collaborative approach between the Centre and the States to ensure balanced growth and political harmony. This study aims to examine the core principles of Indian federalism, analyze its functioning in the current scenario, and identify challenges to cooperative federalism in India. The study will also propose measures to strengthen Centre-State relations within the federal framework. Secondary data will be gathered from research journals, official sources, the writings of prominent legal experts, and other relevant publications.

Keywords: Federalism, Centre-State Relations, Indian Constitution, Power Sharing, Cooperative Federalism, Fiscal Autonomy, Goods and Services Tax (GST), Centralization, State Autonomy, Coalition Politics

1. Introduction

Federalism, as a governance model, distributes power between central and regional entities, ensuring unity while accommodating diversity. In India, a quasi-federal structure was adopted to address its vast geographical, cultural, and linguistic diversity. The Indian Constitution, enacted in 1950, establishes a federal framework with a strong unitary bias, vesting significant authority in the Centre. Over the decades, Centre-State relations have evolved through constitutional amendments, judicial interpretations, and shifting political landscapes. As of 2025, India's federal structure faces new challenges and opportunities. Economic reforms, digital governance, and regional aspirations have reshaped intergovernmental dynamics. However, tensions over fiscal federalism, legislative overreach, and political centralization persist. This article assesses the current state of Centre-State relations, evaluating the balance between cooperative and competitive federalism, and proposes measures to enhance federal harmony²⁹.

²⁹ Constitution of India, 1950.

2. Constitutional Framework of Indian Federalism

The Indian Constitution delineates powers between the Union and States through three lists in the Seventh Schedule: the Union List, State List, and Concurrent List. The Union exercises authority over subjects like defense, foreign affairs, and currency, while States manage areas such as agriculture, public health, and law enforcement. The Concurrent List allows shared jurisdiction over subjects like education and criminal law. Residuary powers rest with the Centre, reinforcing its dominance.

Key constitutional provisions shaping Centre-State relations include:

- **Article 356:** Enables the imposition of President's Rule in States, often criticized for misuse.
- **Article 246:** Defines the legislative competence of the Union and States.
- **Article 280:** Establishes the Finance Commission to recommend tax devolution and grants.
- **Inter-State Council (Article 263):** Facilitates coordination and dispute resolution.

The Constitution's unitary features, such as the Centre's ability to reorganize State boundaries (Article 3) and the Governor's role as a central appointee, contrast with federal principles, creating a "quasi-federal" system.

3. Historical Evolution of Centre-State Relations

India's federal journey reflects a pendulum swing between centralization and decentralization. In the early decades post-independence, the dominance of the Indian National Congress at both levels minimized conflicts. However, the 1960s saw regional parties gaining prominence, leading to demands for greater State autonomy. The 1970s marked a period of centralization, exemplified by the Emergency (1975–1977) and frequent use of Article 356. The 1980s and 1990s witnessed a shift toward cooperative federalism, driven by coalition governments and economic liberalization. Landmark reforms, such as the 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments (1992), empowered local governments, while the Sarkaria Commission (1988) and Punchhi Commission (2010) provided recommendations to strengthen federalism. The 21st century introduced new dynamics. The Goods and Services Tax (GST), implemented in 2017, restructured fiscal federalism, while initiatives like NITI Aayog (established in 2015) replaced the Planning Commission to foster cooperative governance. However, recent years have seen debates over centralizing tendencies, necessitating a fresh assessment.

4. Current Dynamics of Centre-State Relations

As of 2025, Centre-State relations are shaped by fiscal arrangements, political alignments, institutional mechanisms, and judicial interventions. The following sections analyze these dimensions.

4.1 Fiscal Federalism

Fiscal federalism governs the allocation of financial resources between the Centre and States. The Finance Commission, constituted every five years, recommends tax devolution and grants-in-aid. The 15th Finance Commission (2020–2026) increased the States' share of divisible tax pool to 41%, excluding Jammu and Kashmir due to its reorganization. The GST regime has streamlined indirect taxation but reduced States' fiscal autonomy by subsuming State-specific taxes. Compensation cess delays and disputes over revenue sharing have strained relations. For instance, States like Kerala and Tamil Nadu have voiced concerns over inadequate compensation, highlighting regional disparities. Centrally Sponsored Schemes (CSS) further complicate fiscal dynamics. While CSS aim to address national priorities, States often criticize their rigid guidelines, which limit flexibility. In 2025, debates persist over balancing national objectives with State-specific needs.

4.2 Political and Administrative Relations

Political alignments significantly influence Centre-State relations. States governed by opposition parties often experience tensions with the Centre. For example, in 2023–2024, conflicts arose between the

Centre and States like West Bengal and Delhi over issues like fund allocation and administrative control. The role of Governors has been contentious. Governors, as central appointees, occasionally act contrary to State governments' interests, leading to accusations of partisan behavior. The Supreme Court's rulings, such as in *S.R. Bommai v. Union of India* (1994), have curtailed misuse of Article 356, but concerns over gubernatorial overreach remain. NITI Aayog has emerged as a platform for cooperative federalism, fostering dialogue through initiatives like the Governing Council meetings. However, its advisory role limits its effectiveness compared to the erstwhile Planning Commission.

4.3 Legislative and Policy Dynamics

The Centre's legislative dominance, particularly in Concurrent List subjects, often leads to friction. The passage of farm laws in 2020 (later repealed) sparked protests, with States arguing they encroached on agricultural policy, a state subject. Similarly, the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) and National Education Policy (NEP) faced resistance from States citing inadequate consultation. In 2025, digital governance initiatives, such as the Digital India program, have centralized data management, raising concerns over State autonomy in areas like health and education databases. Conversely, cooperative efforts, such as the PM GatiShakti infrastructure plan, demonstrate successful Centre-State collaboration.

4.4 Judicial Interventions

The judiciary plays a pivotal role in mediating Centre-State disputes. The Supreme Court has upheld federal principles in cases like *State of West Bengal v. Union of India* (1963), affirming the federal structure's sanctity. Recent rulings have addressed issues like GST disputes and State borrowing limits, reinforcing constitutional checks and balances. In 2024, the Supreme Court's verdict on State taxation powers clarified the division of fiscal authority, strengthening States' positions. Judicial interventions continue to shape the federal equilibrium, ensuring neither entity dominates unduly.

5. Challenges to Indian Federalism

Several challenges undermine effective Centre-State relations in 2025:

1. **Centralization Trends:** Policies perceived as centralizing, such as the abrogation of Article 370 and uniform national frameworks, spark resistance from States seeking autonomy.
2. **Fiscal Imbalances:** Regional disparities in revenue generation and central transfers exacerbate tensions, with economically weaker States feeling marginalized.
3. **Political Polarization:** Divergent political ideologies between the Centre and States hinder consensus-building, as seen in disputes over law enforcement and public order.
4. **Institutional Weaknesses:** The Inter-State Council and NITI Aayog lack binding authority, limiting their ability to resolve conflicts.
5. **Emerging Issues:** Climate change, cybersecurity, and public health crises require coordinated responses, but differing priorities complicate collaboration.

6. Case Studies

6.1 GST Implementation

The GST regime exemplifies both cooperation and conflict. While it unified India's tax structure, States lost autonomy over indirect taxes. Delays in compensation payments during 2020–2023 led to protests from States like Maharashtra and Punjab. Recent improvements in GST collections (₹2.1 trillion monthly average in 2024) have eased tensions, but States demand greater flexibility in rate-setting.

6.2 COVID-19 Response

The COVID-19 pandemic (2020–2022) tested federal coordination. The Centre imposed nationwide lockdowns, while States managed health infrastructure and vaccination drives. Disparities in resource

allocation and vaccine distribution led to friction, but initiatives like the CoWIN platform showcased successful collaboration.

6.3 Delhi's Administrative Conflict

The tussle between the Delhi government and the Centre over administrative control highlights federal tensions in Union Territories. The Government of NCT Act, 2021, strengthened the Lieutenant Governor's authority, prompting legal challenges. The Supreme Court's ongoing deliberations underscore the need for clarity in federal arrangements.

7. Cooperative vs. Competitive Federalism

Cooperative federalism emphasizes collaboration through institutions like NITI Aayog and schemes like Ayushman Bharat. Competitive federalism, promoted through rankings like the Ease of Doing Business index, encourages States to innovate. However, excessive competition can widen regional disparities, necessitating a balanced approach.

In 2025, initiatives like the Aspirational Districts Programme demonstrate cooperative federalism, while State-led innovations in renewable energy reflect competitive federalism. Striking a balance remains critical to addressing India's diverse needs.

8. Recommendations

To strengthen Indian federalism, the following reforms are proposed:

1. **Enhance Fiscal Autonomy:** Increase States' share in tax devolution and allow flexibility in GST rate-setting for select goods.
2. **Strengthen Institutions:** Grant statutory powers to the Inter-State Council and enhance NITI Aayog's dispute-resolution role.
3. **Reform Governor's Role:** Establish clear guidelines to ensure Governors act as neutral constitutional heads.
4. **Promote Inclusive Policymaking:** Mandate consultations with States on Concurrent List legislation to avoid conflicts.
5. **Address Regional Disparities:** Allocate additional grants to economically weaker States to reduce fiscal imbalances.
6. **Leverage Technology:** Develop digital platforms for real-time Centre-State coordination on issues like disaster management.

9. Conclusion

Indian federalism, with its quasi-federal character, navigates a complex interplay of cooperation and competition. While constitutional provisions and institutional mechanisms provide a robust framework, challenges like centralization, fiscal disputes, and political polarization persist. As of 2025, Centre-State relations reflect both progress and friction, with cooperative initiatives coexisting alongside competitive tensions.

By addressing institutional weaknesses, enhancing fiscal autonomy, and fostering inclusive policymaking, India can strengthen its federal structure. A balanced approach, rooted in mutual respect and collaboration, is essential to realizing the vision of cooperative federalism while accommodating the nation's diverse aspirations.

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FROM TRADITION TO MODERNITY: THE EVOLUTION OF WOMEN'S RIGHTS IN INDIA

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Theme of the study : to understand the status of women rights in India, major legal frameworks, judgements and to study the potential challenges and strategies to overcome the issues associated to women's rights in India.

Abstract

The status and rights of women in India have undergone significant transformations over centuries. From the Vedic era when women enjoyed considerable freedom and respect to the medieval period marked by patriarchal dominance and marginalization and finally to modern times characterized by a struggle for gender equality. The trajectory of women's rights in India reflects a blend of progress and persistent struggles, with ongoing efforts to bridge the gap between legal rights and societal realities. Women's rights in India have reflected broader societal changes. This paper will examine the evolution of women's rights in India through historical, social, legal and political lenses by analyzing key moments and legislative milestones including ongoing challenges.

Keywords: Women's Rights, Patriarchal dominance, Gender equality, Legislation

Introduction

In India Women's rights have evolved alongside the Indian historical cultural and Socio-political dynamics. The concept of women's rights in India is shaped by the interplay of tradition, religion, colonial influences and modern democratic values. During ancient times Indian women were often revered as symbols of strength and divinity. The status of women eroded in subsequent periods like foreign invasions, rhetoric caste structures and patriarchal ideologies. With the advent of the colonial period and the independent movement, significant strides were made towards women's empowerment and development. The history of women's rights in India can be divided into three phases the first face is the beginning of mid 19th century which was initiated when reformists began to raise their voices in favour of women's rights by making women reforms in education customs. The second phase began from 1920 to Indian Independence when the great freedom fighters like Mahatma Gandhi incorporated women's movements. Finally, the third phase is post-independence which focuses on the fair treatment of women at home after marriage and in the workplace

In this paper, an attempt is made to trace the evolution of women's rights and examine its contemporary relevance.

Objectives

- To understand the historical context of women's rights in India
- To examine the legislative provisions to safeguard women's rights in post- independence India
- To explore the potential challenges and strategies to overcome issues associated to women rights.

Status of women's rights in ancient India

During the Vedic period, women in India enjoyed considerable freedom and respect. Rigveda describes women as scholars, poets and philosophers. Practice such as swayamvara highlights their autonomy. Upanishad references women as participants in religious rituals and education. Prominent figures like Gargi and Maitreyi exemplify the intellectual power of women. The status of women was

deteriorated during the later Vedic period. The principle of patriarchy became entrenched and women's roles were increasingly confined to domestic spheres. The Manusmriti codified gender hierarchies emphasizing women's dependence on male relatives.

Status of women's rights in medieval India

The medieval period in India witnessed further erosion of women's rights due to foreign invasion and the entrenchment of patriarchal norms. Practices like Purdah, child marriage and Sati became widespread. However cultural movements such as Bhakti and Sufi tradition challenged these norms offering women-related spaces for expression. Mirabai and Razia Sultana emerged as exceptions in an otherwise restrictive era.

The status of women's rights during colonial India

The colonial period marked the beginning of reform movements addressing women's issues. British legal frameworks combined with Indian reformer's efforts led to significant changes. Social reformers like Raja Ram Mohan Roy Eshwarachandra Vidyasagar, Jyoti Rao Phule and Savitri Bai Phule advocated for women's education, widow remarriage and the abolition of Sati. The enactment of laws such as the Sati Prevention Act (1829) the Widow Remarriage Act (1856), Child Marriage Restraint Act (1929) marked early legal milestones. Indian women witnessed in participation of freedom struggle leaders like Sarojini Naidu, Annie Besant and Kasturba Gandhi challenged the general norms by participating in political activism. This period saw the emergence of a national consciousness about gender equality.

Evolution of women's rights during the post-independence era

Indian constitution adopted in 1950, guaranteed equality, non-discrimination and affirmative action for women under articles 14,15,16, and article 39(d) of the Directive Principles of State Policy emphasized gender justice. The Constitution guarantees equal rights and opportunities for women in all fields and prevents them from being exploited. During garments policy formulation the stress was given to the promotion of women's education and make them aware about their rights and constitutional safeguards. The women's participation in economic activities especially getting entry into the governmental higher positions considerably increased. So sure economic and educational status of women during post-independence pushed them into greater political participation. Major legal provisions made them feel secure and enjoy equal status with men.

Legal milestones

Indian government has passed many milestones to remove the barriers and Women Empowerment status women's rights

- The Hindu Marriage Act (1955) provided equal rights in marriage and divorce
- The Hindu Succession Act (1956 amended in 2005) ensured equal inheritance rights of women.
- The Hindu adoption and Maintenance Act (1956) provides childless women to adopt and divorced women to seek maintenance from their husband
- Dowry Prohibition Act (1961) criminalized the practice of dowry
- Equal Remuneration Act (1976) ensured equal pay for equal work
- The Protection of women from Domestic Violence Act (2005) protects women from domestic abuse.
- Prohibition of Child Marriage Act (2006) raised the legal marriage age
- The sexual harassment of women at work workplace Act (2013) defined and penalized workplace harassment.

Judicial interventions

Indian Judiciary has played a crucial role in interpreting laws to empower women. Some of the landmark judgments are given as follows.

- Visakha v. State of Rajasthan (1997) laid guidelines for workplace harassment.
- Shayara Bano v. Union of India (2017) declared triple talaq unconstitutional
- Joseph Shine v. Union of India (2018) Decriminalised adultery by striking down section 497 of the Indian penal code and promoted gender equality in marital relationships.

Contemporary issues and challenges

Indian women have been an integral part of our culture and Society since time immemorial. Despite progress, gender inequality and multifaceted issues persist in India. Major challenges are as follows

- **Gender-Based Violence:** Due to insufficient law enforcement, delays in judicial processes and victim support systems in India we are witnessing high rates of domestic violence rape honour killing as an attack and human trafficking. According to the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), crimes against women continue to rise, with a significant increase in reported cases of rape and sexual assault.
- **Economic Disparities:** Women in India are significantly less than men for the same work across industries. Cultural Expectations lack of childcare support and unsafe working environments limit the economic independence of women to exercise their rights.
- **Access to Education:** India's made several girl child enrolments at the early school level. Even though gender disparity in school environments particularly in rural areas is visible. Early dropper rates due to child marriage poverty and societal norms discouraging female education.
- **Cultural and Social Norms:** deeply rooted patriarchal attitudes continue to restrict women's freedom and autonomy in decision-making. Intersectionality of gender caste and religion exacerbate discrimination. Child marriages are still prevalent in rural areas.
- **Political Representation:** women remain underrepresented in Legislative bodies. Women's issues often remain under prioritized in policymaking due to a lack of party support and cultural resistance to women's leadership.

Strategies to Overcome Challenges

In recent years government has made many positive developments in India to empower women's status. During policy formulation, significant efforts are at to improve women's education health and economic opportunities. Here are some suggestions for improving access to women's rights.

- **Stronger Law Enforcement:** Training police and judiciary to handle women's issues sensitively and expedite legal processes.
- **Education Initiatives:** Improving access to education for girls, especially in rural areas, through scholarships and infrastructure development.
- **Economic Empowerment:** Promoting women's entrepreneurship, vocational training, and creating safer workplaces.
- **Healthcare Access:** Strengthening healthcare systems to ensure affordable reproductive and maternal healthcare.
- **Cultural Shifts:** Using media and education to challenge patriarchal norms and promote gender equality.
- **Technology Access:** Bridging the digital divide by providing affordable devices and digital literacy programs for women.

Conclusion

Women's rights in India have undergone significant evolution, shaped by a combination of traditional norms, colonial influences, and modern legal and social reforms. The awareness about women's rights in India has improved significantly in recent years but there is still a long way to go. By addressing contemporary challenges through a combination of policy, education, and societal reform, India can take significant strides toward achieving gender equality and safeguarding women's rights. The evolution of women's rights in India reflects a broader struggle for equality in a complex socio-cultural context, while significant progress has been made on the journey towards full gender parity. Empowerment of women requires sustained legal, social and political efforts alongside a commitment to challenge deep rooted patriarchal mindset. While constitutional and legislative frameworks have paved the way for gender equality, societal latitudes and systemic barriers continue to impair progress. Achieving substantive equality requires a multifaceted approach combining legal reforms, policy frameworks and cultural transformation as India progresses the empowerment of women will be crucial to realizing it's democratic ideal.

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REGIONAL PARTIES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON INDIAN FEDERALISM**Sneha Naresh Kulkarni**

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Abstract

India's federal structure is a delicate balance between central and state powers, with regional parties playing a significant role in shaping the country's political landscape. These parties, representing the interests of specific regions, have increasingly influenced national policy decisions, particularly in a multi-party, coalition-driven political environment. This paper aims to analyze the role of regional parties in Indian federalism, examining how they affect the distribution of powers, the dynamics of coalition politics, and the balance between the center and states. By exploring case studies of key regional parties such as the Trinamool Congress (TMC), Dravida Munnetra Kazhagam (DMK), Samajwadi Party (SP), and others, this paper evaluates how these parties influence national governance, federal relations, and policy-making processes. The paper argues that while regional parties have been crucial in promoting federalism and regional aspirations, they also present challenges to national unity, political stability, and governance.

• Introduction

India, as a federal union of states, is built on a constitutional framework that seeks to balance power between the central government and the states. The Indian Constitution, while granting significant autonomy to states, envisions a strong central government with a focus on national integration and unity. However, over time, regional parties have gained substantial traction in both state and national politics, altering the dynamics of Indian federalism. These parties have emerged not only as champions of regional autonomy but also as key players in national politics, often participating in coalition governments at the center. This paper explores the role and influence of regional parties in shaping the federal fabric of India.

• The Role of Regional Parties in Indian Federalism**1. Historical Context of Indian Federalism**

The Indian Union was designed to accommodate a diverse set of regional, linguistic, and cultural identities. The federal structure was intended to provide a platform for states to assert their rights and manage local affairs, while ensuring national unity. Initially, national parties like the Indian National Congress (INC) dominated both state and central politics. However, by the 1960s and 1970s, regional parties began emerging as important political forces in various states.

2. Regional Parties and their Rise in Indian Politics

Decentralization and Regional Identity: With the decline of the Congress dominance and the rise of regional parties, the Indian political landscape began to reflect the growing demands for regional autonomy. Parties such as the TMC in West Bengal, DMK in Tamil Nadu, and Shiv Sena in Maharashtra started to shape local and national policies. **Coalition Governments and the Role of Regional Parties:** The 1980s and 1990s marked the rise of coalition politics, where regional parties played a pivotal role in the formation of national governments. Their participation in coalitions at the center has influenced key policy decisions, from economic reforms to foreign policy.

3. Regional Parties and National Policy

Regional parties often assert their regional identities and interests, pressuring the central government to accommodate local demands. This can be seen in the push for federal financial devolution, demands for autonomy in areas like education, language, and culture, and regional development agendas.

example, the demand for a special status for Jammu and Kashmir, the push for autonomy by parties like the TMC and AIADMK, and the DMK's advocacy for Tamil language rights are all emblematic of regional aspirations shaping national policy.

4. Impact on Federal Relations and Governance

Balancing Power: Regional parties have often challenged the centralizing tendencies of the Indian state. This has brought attention to the need for a more equitable distribution of powers and resources between the central government and the states.
Inter-State Relations: The growing prominence of regional parties has led to better representation of state interests in the national political discourse. However, this has also led to tensions between states and the center, as regional parties assert more autonomy, sometimes at odds with national interests.

- **Political Stability:** The role of regional parties in coalition governments is double-edged. On the one hand, they bring more inclusive representation; on the other hand, they can lead to political instability due to ideological differences or demands that may not align with the central government's priorities.

5. Regional Parties and the Challenge to National Unity

While regional parties promote regional identities and demands, they can also fuel regionalism that poses a threat to national unity. Their advocacy for state rights often extends to demands for greater autonomy, which, in some cases, can lead to secessionist sentiments or exacerbate inter-state rivalries. The role of regional parties in demanding state-specific policies sometimes leads to friction between states with differing interests, such as disputes over water-sharing, language issues, and economic disparities.

- **Case Studies of Key Regional Parties**

1. Trinamool Congress (TMC)

The TMC, under Mamata Banerjee, has emerged as a formidable force in West Bengal and a key player in national politics. The party has often played a critical role in national coalition politics, advocating for greater autonomy for states and regional development. The TMC's vocal opposition to the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP)-led central government has led to intense debates over federalism and governance.

2. Dravida Munnetra Kazhagam (DMK)

The DMK has been a key political player in Tamil Nadu for decades, with a strong focus on regional identity and autonomy. The party's demand for linguistic and cultural rights for Tamils and its insistence on preserving the rights of states in federal governance have significantly impacted the discourse on Indian federalism.

3. Shiv Sena

A regional party based in Maharashtra, the Shiv Sena has influenced both state and national politics. Initially focused on the interests of the Marathi-speaking population, the party's role in the coalition politics of India has often highlighted the tension between regionalism and national unity.

4. Samajwadi Party (SP)

Based in Uttar Pradesh, the SP has consistently advocated for policies catering to the state's rural and backward classes. The party's role in national politics, especially in coalition governments, has raised questions about the role of caste-based politics in federalism and governance.

- **Conclusion**

Regional parties have undoubtedly played a crucial role in the evolution of Indian federalism, advocating for regional interests and ensuring that diverse voices are heard in the national political arena. While their influence has been instrumental in ensuring more balanced federal relations, it has

also raised challenges in terms of national cohesion, political stability, and governance. The future of Indian federalism will depend on how effectively the central government and regional parties can navigate these complexities, ensuring that regional aspirations are met while preserving the integrity and unity of the Indian Union. The dynamics of coalition politics, state autonomy, and national governance will continue to evolve as regional parties remain influential in shaping the country's political and federal landscape.

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EXPLORING MODERNITY THROUGH CRITIQUE: U.R. ANANTHAMURTHY'S PERSPECTIVES AND PHILOSOPHIES

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Abstract

U R Ananthamurthy is regarded as one of the eminent writers not only in Karnataka but also at the national level. His versatile writing has made him more popular. His literary works include novels, short stories and poems. Although he is mainly seen as a writer, he also finds a place among the intellectual fraternity that Karnataka has seen. Though his novels mainly depict progressive modern ideas, it can also be seen that he has expressed his reservations about the consequences of modernity in many of his writings. In this backdrop, this paper explores ananthamurthy's profound engagement with modernity by criticizing the socio-political and cultural aspects of Indian society. Through a close reading of his major works such as Samskara, Bharathipura and some of his essays, this paper examines how Ananthamurthy questions and redefines modernity by reclaiming it through an Indian perspective. His essays expose the dark side of the development that is going on in the name of modernity. His writings also focus on the disparity caused by the economic policies of this modern age which has resulted in making various languages and cultures to reach a state of losing their identity. Overall, this article attempts to present the perspectives of Ananthamurthy as a critique of modernity and their significance.

Keywords: *Gandhian thought, Cultural identity, Social hierarchies, Post-colonial societies, Spiritual science, Western model*

Introduction:

U.R. Ananthamurthy is one of the greatest writers and intellectuals of Karnataka. He was a vivid personality who never shied away from expressing his opinion. He was not limited to literature as a mere writer, but was responsive to everyday social, political and cultural issues. He was vocal in criticizing the rituals and traditions practiced by the society. His childhood environment had a profound influence in shaping his views.

. Ananthamurthy, who unflinchingly expressed his opinions based on his deeply studied ideas, was recognized in the intellectual and public circles for his boldness. Ananthamurthy was exposed to the ideas of modernity in his childhood and was later influenced by socialism, Gandhianism and Marxism. This also had a profoundly influenced his writings and thoughts. Ananthamurthy who initially expressed progressive modernist ideas in his writings, mainly in his novels, at a later period was concerned about the dark side of modernity and its effects on the social, political and cultural system of India.

Discussion

An Overview of Ananthamurthy's Perspectives:

U.R. Ananthamurthy, the renowned Kannada writer and Jnanpitha awardee, is often known for his distinctive critique of modernity – a view that largely evolved over his lifetime. Initially Ananthamurthy's modern ideas were shaped by progressive and secular ideologies which included rationality, social reform, eradicating class disparities and breaking down caste hierarchies. However, his perspective changed over a period of time and he began to critique certain aspects of modernity, questioning the impact of westernized concept of modernization on Indian society.

Ananthamurthy's critique of modernity is multi-layered which is a confluence of Gandhian thought, spiritual traditions of India and the western concept of existentialism. It provides a nuanced perspective on the consequences of adopting the forces of modernity namely erosion of cultural identity and moral ambiguities. He also warns of the socio-political repercussions of accepting western model of modernity unquestionably.

The Critique of Modernity in Novels:

Critical engagement of Ananthamurthy with modernity can be seen in his most famous work *Samskara*. Set in an agrahara, novel gives us an illustration of what happens when traditional values face modern ethical questions. In *Samskara*, Ananthamurthy depicts a culturally decaying society. On one side are the members of this society who blindly follow the customs and traditions while on the other side Praneshacharya is in awe of the debate regarding the death of Naranappa in Agrahara which leads to a conflict between tradition and modernity. The novel examines the conflicts between the traditional values upheld by that society and the moral questions of modernity that have arisen after Narayanappa's death.

Praneshacharya, the protagonist of the novel, is caught in the duality between the responsibility of protecting the traditions followed by the Agrahara on one side and on the other side he needs to go through the process of social change that is inevitable.

“There's only one way out of the present fear. I must take on the responsibility of Naranappa's last rites. I must stand upright in the eyes of the Brahmins, in the very agrahara where I grew up to be respected, an elder. Must call in Garuda and Lakshmana and tell them: “This is how it went. My decision is such and such. I'll shed the respectability I acquired here before your eyes.” If I don't, my fear will dog me everywhere, I won't be free. What then?” (Ananthamurthy 1978, 131)

‘Ananthamurthy's nuanced representation of Praneshacharya's spiritual crisis exemplifies the writer's critique of both blind adherence to tradition and uncritical acceptance of modernity. The novel questions whether modernity, if unadopted to local culture, can foster a truly ethical society, or if it merely erodes the moral fabric without offering viable alternatives’ (Murthy, 2013).

In his works such as *Bharatipura* and *Avasthe*, Ananthamurthy highlights the socio-political aspects exhibiting how modernity, instead of eliminating caste and social hierarchies, sometimes reinforces them. It shows a paradigm shift from his earlier stand whereby he sees modernity, not as a solution to the social evils but, as a perpetuator of disparities. It has resulted in alienation and erosion of cultural values.

“Look, how did you do it?” Manjunatha became convinced that the Harijans would come in - thus the news spread among the people. Sri Neelakanthaswamy announced from the microphone that it was Ganesh Bhatta, son of the priests, who removed the Linga. But people danced in joy thinking that Bhutaraya occupied the body of Sri Ganeshbhatta and had thrown Manjunatha into the water the previous night so that the temple would not be polluted by the entry of the holeyas.” (Ananthamurthy 2008, 203)

Ananthamurthy's Philosophical Foundations and Gandhian Influence:

Gandhi had a profound influence on Ananthamurthy from his childhood days, both in his writings as well as thought. Mahatma Gandhi's principles, particularly his skepticism towards modern civilization and industrialization, had a great impact in shaping U.R. Ananthamurthy as a critique of modernity. He often brings Gandhiji's idea of decentralization, self-reliant society, Swaraj, non-violence in his writings to overcome the ill-effects of modernity.

Ananthamurthy's stand regarding modernity changed in the later stage from that of a staunch supporter to that of a critique. He engages with the ideals of modernity but is wary of the ill effects it could bring upon the traditional Indian society. This view of Ananthamurthy is in tune with that of Mahatma Gandhi who advocated modernity rooted in indigenous values rather than western ideals.

Gandhiji had a critical view of modern civilization, which tends to be materialistic as well as exploitative. Ananthamurthy reiterated Gandhiji's ideas in his essay 'India in 2062: An Idea'.

"After almost three decades ago when the entire world came to the brink of annihilation due to the senseless consumer culture and the idea of development that we have been indoctrinated into the illusion of modern civilization, till now, we have to remember these words of Gandhiji again and again and find ways to escape from the danger." (Ananthamurthy 2015, 40)

'Thus life became tiring and monotonous. As a result, a spiritual and cultural imperative was created to re-examine the anthropocentric superstition of modern civilization about the idea of mighty nations and the earth as a melting pot. As a result, India did not need a centralized power or an army for defense in the decentralized village republics of 30 years ago. When the whole country is like a porcupine, which is ready to jump on it?' (Ananthamurthy 2015, 41)

According to Ananthamurthy, 'the greatest transition in the idea of India from mythology to politics and history was done by Mahatma Gandhi. But Gandhi did not completely abandon the idea of mythology without revising it.' (Ananthamurthy 2007, 48)

In his essay titled 'Modern Civilization and the Status of the Cow', Ananthamurthy says "What Gandhi wanted was not the product of modern civilization; A product of many people. Agriculture-based way of life in India involves many people in production." (Ananthamurthy 2015, 124)

Gandhiji objects to violence in any form because it perpetuates hatred. Concurring with Gandhiji's philosophy, Ananthamurthy in his essay describes how development incites violence. "The violence now being done in the name of development is no less in terms of destruction of ways of life than the violence perpetrated by Hitler in Germany. Even Stalin in Russia did all violence for development. The violence in China is for this development. The same is happening in India. So we need to reexamine this development, the enormous, unnecessary sacrifices it demands." (Ananthamurthy 2021, 81)

Postcolonial Concerns and Cultural Identity:

Ananthamurthy was critical of the western ideals, imposed by the colonialism, that have disrupted the indigenous traditions and values. In this regard, he calls for an introspection of modernity in post-colonial India by critically evaluating and selectively adapting the western practices without abandoning their deep rooted cultural values.

Addressing the effects of modernity on local cultures, Ananthamurthy tells us that 'whatever communal India is, it kills the spirit of innovation in our religions. Both rootless modernism and extreme radical communalism undermine the sense of myth in the people of India.' (Ananthamurthy 2015, 49) In the rush to embrace modernity, he cautions us not to forget our diversity and originality.

"But in such nation building process we should not abandon our multiculturalism as well as Advaita philosophy which is the foundation of our culture. It is true that we should not fall behind when the whole world is moving forward. But we must not lose sight of where the power of our existence lies in the process of development. ." (Ananthamurthy 2015, 69)

Every nation under the influence of modernity is today prone to the establishment of multinational companies. Ananthamurthy expresses concern over its negative impact on the basic culture, customs and ideas of those nations. "The only thing that is happening with all these changes of

governments is how and how fast they can create the most favorable system for the multinational companies here. My fear in the process of creating this favorable system is that it will change our food habits, dress code, our languages, our manners, even among the educated people, if we can survive in this country as a civilization. This is the change the ruling class is making within itself. But because this change can become a pattern for the less fortunate, I call it a frightening change.” (Ananthamurthy 2021, 22)

“For thousands of years, even in the midst of all the pressure and necessity, some people have not lost the wisdom to know what is wrong and what is right, that is what we call spiritual science. It seems to be fading in India now. (Ananthamurthy 2021, 49)

Ananthamurthy’s Unique model:

Ananthamurthy’s views and ideas on modernity suggest a hybrid form i.e., a blend of both western and local ideals. It is a unique model that respects the local traditions and progressive changes. This is illustrated in his essay titled ‘Towards a New Nation Idea: Indian Languages and Literatures’, where he says “Creativity is unfolding in a new way in India. A necessary anti-traditional attitude is now evident in all our literary works. Here is also the idea of the identity of communities that lived with cultural contrasts and cultural hybrids.” (Ananthamurthy 2015, 61)

Relevance of Ananthamurthy’s Perspectives Today:

Ananthamurthy’s perspectives seem to be highly relevant in this era of globalization as they address the serious problem of identity crisis faced by the post-colonial societies. His writings involve debates on globalization, localization and cultural homogenization which call for a critical evaluation of modernity. Ananthamurthy is deeply concerned about the adaption of modernity in various fields without looking at the consequences it might bring in the future. By interrogating modernity through his narratives, Ananthamurthy provides readers with a means to question dominant paradigms and consider alternative visions of progress (Sarkar, 2018).

Regardless of the problems that modernity may bring and pose, we are experimenting with modernity in various fields today. Ananthamurthy warns that we will have to bear the consequences. We are following the western model in the name of modernity which is leading to the destruction of customs, ideas and cultures of this land. Ananthamurthy expressed his concern that our diversity is being destroyed and the languages and cultures are losing their identity. In this direction, he emphasizes the need for all of us to rethink about the idea of modernity.

“We also need modernization; is it possible that the cow should remain sacred? Those who question the dams we build for modernization, nuclear plants, the nuclear bombs we detonate under the pretext of state security, and those who question our farming using chemical fertilizers are seen as traitors to us.” (Ananthamurthy 2021, 125)

Emphasizing on the value of our ancient traditional methods, Ananthamurthy says “The ancient religions were keenly aware that the source of the human spirit, as much as it lay in the dreams of later development, lay in the all-pervading inspiration of man. It is because of this knowledge that our traditional methods of agriculture and medicine were born. In our time we have to remember all that we have forgotten in the arrogance of technology’. (Ananthamurthy 2017, 157)

Warning about the future problems of environmental destruction in the name of development, Ananthamurthy says “There is no obstacle to human progress; it was the fruit of 18th and 19th century European thought that the earth could satisfy all human appetites like a pot. Perhaps we cannot think rigorously about the environment unless we let go of this idea of continuous development.” (Ananthamurthy 2015, 156)

Conclusion:

U.R. Ananthamurthy's critique of modernity is deeply rooted in Indian philosophy and reflects post-colonial anxieties. Also his critique of modernity was influenced by Gandhiji's ideologies. His views Present a valuable perspective on how societies can navigate the challenges of modernization. His works suggest that true progress lies in critically embracing modernity while preserving cultural identity and moral integrity. Ananthamurthy's perspectives offer contemporary readers a framework for engaging with modernity in a way that respects individual freedom and collective cultural values.

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SWAMI VIVEKANANDA'S VISION OF NATIONALISM: INTEGRATING SPIRITUALITY AND UNITY IN INDIA**Divya R**

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Abstract

Swami Vivekananda was a great spiritual thinker and father of Indian spiritual nationalism. Swami Vivekananda was proud of the Indian heritage, culture and its spirituality. While many modern thinkers say that religion is the cause of India's problems, Swami Vivekananda says that improper understanding of the religion is the reason for India's problems. He gave a unique concept of nationalism which is quite different from the westernized concept of nationalism. In this backdrop, this article discusses the westernized concept of nationalism and the idea of spiritual nationalism as put forward by Swami Vivekananda. Although Swami Vivekananda does not deny the elements of nationalism as expressed in the western concept but in the case of India, he makes spirituality as the basis of Indian nationalism. It was his strong belief that the common element that can achieve nationalism in India is the spirituality. This paper focusses on Swami Vivekananda's views on religion and its significance in achieving nationalism in India. It also sheds light on his thoughts regarding universal love and importance of spirituality. Overall, this paper attempts to find the importance of the idea of spiritual nationalism and also how this idea suits a country like India where pluralism exists.

Key Words: *Common race, Pluralism, Universal love, Spiritual unity, life blood, Religion*

Introduction

Swami Vivekananda held a great place in the history of Indian nationalism. In his short span of life, he gave a profound form to nationalism by giving it a spiritual dimension. Swami Vivekananda's biggest contribution to political thought is his theory of Spiritual nationalism. In 1893, he took part in the world's parliament of Religions held in Chicago where he delivered his lecture which proved to be extremely popular.

Vivekananda identifies India's ancient spiritual heritage as the foundation of India's national identity. He believed that Indians could rise above colonial oppression and social divisions by re-establishing their self-respect and self-confidence. In Vivekananda's view, true nationalism is that which includes all and unites all without distinction of caste, creed and language.

Methodology:

This is primarily an interdisciplinary research, encompassing the fields of Philosophy and Political Science. It is purely based on qualitative research methodology adopting descriptive as well as analytical approaches. The study has its primary resources in the works of Swami Vivekananda and web articles. The research also relies upon secondary resources which include books, journal articles and e-resources.

Discussion:**Concept of Nationalism:**

Politically nationalism is an ideology whereas psychologically it is an attitude which teaches the loyalty, devotion and sacrifices of its people towards a nation. Nationalism refers to the pride of the people living in a nation and the feeling that it is mine. Some thinkers argue that it is this feeling that brings people together and makes them work towards achieving a particular goal.

Economic power alone cannot make a nation great and strong. Instead, the feeling among the people of a nation that we all are one can make a nation strong. True power must be born from within. Thus nationalism has its own significance.

Nationalism can be characterized as the attitude of self-determination of a particular nation by claiming sovereignty over the geographical area in which it lives with inalienable ties. Nationalism can be identified as an inseparable relationship with one's race and their customs.

Nationalism, as expressed in political theory, consists of many elements, namely common race, language, religion, traditions, history, geography. But the situation in India is quite opposite to the ideological concept of nationalism. In other words, Swami Vivekananda is the one who brought the concept of nationalism to the world to bring together many races, religions, clans, sects, languages, customs and ideas and create a feeling that we are all one.

Swami Vivekananda's concept of Nationalism:**Spiritual Foundation:**

Swami Vivekananda does not deny the elements of nationalism such as common race, common language, common history, common religion and common economic interests as presented in the political theory. But in the case of India, he makes spirituality as the basis of Indian nationalism. It was his strong belief that the common element that can achieve nationalism by uniting many castes, races, languages, customs and creeds that exist in India is the spirituality. That is, the essence of Indian continent is in spirituality. This is the foundation of the nation, on which the national edifice rests. Vivekananda strongly advocated nationalism with a spiritual dimension saying that spirituality is the link that unites us all.

“The edifice of the nation rests on the foundation of spirituality. You and I are truly one. This is the Indian doctrine. This oneness is the foundation of all spirituality and ethics” (CWSV Vol. 3, P.61)

Vivekananda relates religion/spirituality with India's national identity. His political importance resides in how he provided spiritual basis to nationalism. Philosophically and theologically he was probably the most influential co-founder of a modern re-reading of Advaita Vedanta known as neo-vedanta. Vivekananda became one of the architects of Neo-vedanta and a pioneer of spiritual nationalism.

“We are so many sanyasins wandering about and teaching the people metaphysics – it is all madness. Did not our Gurudeva use to say: “An empty stomach is no good for religion”? That those poor people are living the life of brutes is simply due to ignorance. We as a nation have lost our individuality and that is the cause of all mischief in India. We have to give back the nation its lost individuality and raise the masses.” (CWSV VI, P 254)

He gave importance to worldly and spiritual life and up-liftment of the masses. Vivekananda said that India would one day conquer the world with its religious and spiritual knowledge. Vivekananda's firm belief was that both physical development and spiritual development should go hand in hand. He recognized that in the present age it is necessary for us to have a realistic outlook on the one hand and deep spiritual knowledge on the other.

According to Vivekananda, "Spirituality is our life blood. If it is pure, if it is nourished, all the political, social and other worldly grievances as well as the misery of our country will be removed. Religion is our brilliance, our strength: the basic wall of national life. Other things are unnecessary. It does not mean that political, social progress is unnecessary. Here they are subservient, here religion is paramount." (CWSV III, P.161-163)

Unity and Oneness:

Swami Vivekananda says that Indians should be proud of their nation, acceptance of pluralism and integration with it are essential elements of nationalism. The strength of any nation lies in its spiritual unity. Vivekananda's nationalism is not physical but spiritual, the source of the nation's strength. Vivekananda never advocated communalism or oppression of Hindus over other religions, as unity among religions would be a good foundation for Indian nationalism and a model for the world. He tried in his own way to create nationalism among Indians based on overall spiritual foundation.

Unity among religions is essential for building a future India. In this background, religion/spirituality based on Advaita Vedanta should be followed because it is based on the basic principles in all religions. It is said that all religions preach the principle of unity in diversity. By following Advaita Vedanta, we can treat all religions with equal love and respect. Thus, he believes that Advaita Vedanta is the religion of future enlightened humanity.

It is the lack of religious unity that has hampered India's nationalism, not religious diversity. Because our life force is spirituality, he advocated a religion incorporating the common principles of the various religions.

The elements of nationalism as expressed in political theory are one race, one language, one history, one religion, common economic interest. But since there are many races, languages, customs, religions in India and multiplicity or plurality is the lifeblood here, the western concept of ethnic nationalism can never apply to us. Rather, "spirituality/religion is the lifeblood of people in the Indian continent; it is the root, the foundation and the leaf on which our nation's building stands." Swami Vivekananda says that India's way of life is based on spirituality and considers spirituality as one of India's strengths and advocates it as the root of nationalism.

According to Vivekananda, "Our nation can be built only by unity. There should be sects and not differences. The world cannot move forward without different sects. Our ancient scriptures say that these differences are not true. Even though there are differences, all of them are united by the principle of unity. Even if we belong to many sects and traditions, yet we all agree on some great basic principles."

That is, according to Vivekananda, the common ground between the many sects in India is the perception of the soul. In other words, Vivekananda recognizes that the basis of nationalism is the spiritual feeling common to all these different religious sects.

According to Vivekananda every country has its own mission (ideal). This is the lifeblood of the nation. The lifeblood of India is not military power, not economic or mechanical hegemony. Religion is our life. National edifice is built on the foundation of spirituality. So let us achieve spiritual unity. We cannot raise our motherland unless we implement this great feeling of unity.

"The problems of the Indian continent are more complicated and serious than the problems of other countries. Race, religion, language, government, all these are combined to become a nation. Arya, Dravida, Turk and Mughal - the blood of all these races is flowing here. Our only common ground is the sacred heritage and religion on which our nation can be built." (CWSV III, P. 160)

It is said that pluralism which is not found in other countries of the world is the specialty of India. The common factor between us is our spiritual heritage and religious unity is essential for the organization of India.

When Vivekananda says that religion is the basis of Indian nationalism, he is not referring to any particular religion. All religions have a common foundation. That is, it is the perception of the soul, and this spiritual feeling is said to be the basis of Indian nationalism.

Moral and Ethical foundation:

Swami Vivekananda's neo-Vedanta gave importance to the unity of God and man. It thereby gave a new dimension to nationalism as spirituality. He gave practical form to Advaita thought. That means God and man are not different. They are both same. Thus he gave importance to selfless service and sacrifice (Karmayoga) by asserting that service to man is service to God. Not only that, he asserted the need for attitudes of tolerance and acceptance by saying that the goal of all religions is the same.

"Progress can only be achieved if all the people of India work together as one nation. When there are people who can give their all for the country, India will be great in every field of work. If there are enthusiastic young people who can make self-sacrifice, it can be done tomorrow. Because what is there in a country? It is the people who build a country..." (CWSV Vol.VII P. 432-433)

For that, our country needs a youth with muscles like iron, nerves like steel and a will that no one can shake. For that it is necessary to properly understand and embody Advaita Vedanta, which gives the message of faith and fearlessness, the essence of unity that sees all as one.

Vivekananda said that we have to be proactive. All of us should give up our weaknesses and become fearless and brave. He said that nation can progress when there are selfless and enthusiastic youth. We as common people should be active. Because India's prosperity can only be achieved if they are saved. In this regard, he said that working hard for the prosperity of the people is more important than paying attention to God. Pluralism should be our philosophy and this should not be denied even today.

Influence of Vivekananda's nationalism on the Indian freedom movement:

Swami Vivekananda's thoughts had a profound influence on the national movement. Subhash Chandra Bose said that although Swami Vivekananda had no political message, those who came into contact with him or were influenced by his writings developed nationalism. He said that he can be called the spiritual father of the modern national movement especially in Bengal. As Sri Aurobindo said "Vivekananda's influence continues to have a great impact even today and he lives on in the soul of Indians in the spirit of the motherland".

V.K.R.V. Rao (1979) in his book, "Builders of Modern India-Swami Vivekananda The Prophet of Vedantic Socialism", said that although Swami Vivekananda was not involved in politics but it cannot be denied that Swami Vivekananda played a significant role in the construction of modern India after Gandhiji. It is said that Gandhi was also influenced by Vivekananda.

Relevance:

India can produce power, science-technology and material appetite like the western countries. But if we do not understand universal love, religion and spirituality in the right sense, we cannot become a co-existing, peaceful and happy nation. Thus, Swami Vivekananda's ideas of spirituality-based nationalism are not limited to his time but have relevance in today's complex world.

Conclusion:

The concept of nationalism as articulated in political theory is a Western concept which is appropriate to the geographical, social, political and cultural conditions there. But the conditions in

India are different and diversity is the lifeblood here. However, if we have to create unity among the Indians that we are all one, it needs a concept of nationalism that is formed in a unique background that does not threaten the conditions here that arose from the soil of India rather than the concept of nationalism that was formed on the western basis. In this background, Swami Vivekananda has put forward the idea of nationalism with the essence of spirituality which preaches unity in the diversity that exists in India.

Findings:

Western popular concept of nationalism emphasizes on common race, language, religion, culture, history as the elements of nationalism. In contrast to this concept, we see the existence of plurality in India. In this direction, Swami Vivekananda has presented to the world the concept of nationalism based on spirituality which preaches unity in diversity.

Suggestions:

While spirituality is related to the supernatural or intellectual, nationalism is related to the worldly or materialistic. While nationalism is about cultivating feelings of love, affection, loyalty, sacrifice, pride towards one's nation or motherland, spirituality is about liberation from all worldly attachments. Against this backdrop, the question arises as to what extent worldly nationalism can be achieved through supernatural spirituality. Because nationalism is a purely secular political concept. Additional study is necessary in this regard.

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DELIMITATION AND DEMOGRAPHY OF NORTH-SOUTH DIVIDE: A GROWING SOUTHERN CONSCIOUSNESS

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Abstract

The Indian federal system that is guided by the constitution believes in the pluralist equitable views, unity and integrity of the nation and decentralized political authority that tilts towards a unitary system than federal. However the powers are divided between the central government and the state governments making it convenient to the states to play a vital role in governing. Article 1 of the constitution emphasizes that "India that is Bharat, shall be a union of States" thus upholding the spirit of the law of the land. But the recent developments in the functioning of the federal system more so of the co-operative federalism, has been undergoing tremendous changes due to various political reasons and delimitation and demography are two such concerns which has paved way for discussions on North-South divide and the growing southern consciousness. The delimitation that has been deferred since 1976 is going to end by 2026 which may reduce the representation of the southern states in the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies, has been seen as a regressive step for the south which may hamper the developmental activities of the states that is co-incidentally linked with the demography of these states. The southern states are far more progressive in containing the population thereby focusing on the development of the states while in some northern states the population has increased, less development is witnessed. Apart from the above in the central governments allocation of funds too, there are vast disparities that has led to a debate on the north-south concerns. This paper focuses mainly on the delimitation and demographical effects on the states that has led to the discussions and deliberations countrywide. The data is gathered from secondary sources and the study is qualitative in nature.

Key words: co-operative federalism, delimitation, demography, development, southern consciousness,

Objectives:

The study focuses on the following objectives:

1. To examine the concept of delimitation and its impact on Indian political system
2. To identify the problems of demography and its influence on north-south states
3. To access and analyze the factors responsible for debates on north-south divide

Methodology:

The paper adopts qualitative method to seek answers to the questions that have been raised in the course of discussions. Also, the paper focuses on content analysis that is used in social science research.

Literature Review:

Rangarajan R (Feb 2024) **Understanding the delimitation exercise**, The Hindu: This review article focuses on the delimitation exercise that was undertaken in 1976 which was due for 2021(as the census 2021) was postponed to 2026 due to covid 19. Delimitation is the process of fixing seats to various constituencies of Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies as delimitation of the constituencies takes place after every census. This article probes into the various aspects of delimitation that was frozen as per 1971 census to encourage population control.

Chethan Choitani, Arslan Wali Khan (August 2024) **Southward Ho!! Demographic change and North South divide, The India Forum**: This article discusses about the dynamics about the work migration in the context of demographic north-south divide as a significant portion of youth reside in the most populated states with less opportunities and its impact on southern states.

Editorial, (June 2023) Daily updates: Complexities of Indian Federalism – This editorial talk about the Indian Federal System and its complexities, issues, challenges, devolution of powers etc., in the present context and highlights the changes that are essential.

Louise Tillin (2019) Indian Federalism, Oxford University Press – This book analyses about the necessity of the federal system in order to protect the center state relations and why is it essential to again protect the economic ecosystem.

Introduction:

Article 1 of the constitution states “India that is Bharat shall be a union of states” and according to the spirit of this, we have accepted a federal system that is in structure but unitary in nature that is often referred to as ‘quasi federal’. In other words “federalism rests on the idea of shared and multi-layered sovereignty” It has enabled the expression and protection of diverse forms of belonging within the country. (Tillin 2019). The framers of the constitution of India adopted the federal system due to two main reasons – large size of the country and its socio-cultural diversity as it can reconcile with national unity and regional autonomy. As the center-state relations progressed there also arose certain challenges which has become very very vital in the present socio-political conditions. The recent debates being the delimitation process and the demographic changes that has led to North-South debates.

Understanding Delimitation:

What is Delimitation?

Delimitation is the process of setting the boundaries or allotting the seats of constituencies for Lok Sabha and State Legislative assemblies. It also includes seats to be reserved for Scheduled Caste (SC) and Scheduled Tribes (ST) in these chambers. Delimitation Commission under Article 82 and 170 of the constitution provides the number of seats in the Lok Sabha and Legislative assemblies enacts a delimitation Act after every census which demarcates the boundaries of the parliamentary constituencies as per the provisions of the Act. In other words it is a process which enables the parliament to either extend or reduce the parliamentary boundaries stipulated by the previous census. The present delimitation of constituencies has been done on the basis of 2001 census, under the Delimitation Act, 2002 which categorically mention that the present constituencies shall continue to be in operation till the census after 2026 (which as amended in the year 2002). This was done after 1951, 1961, 1971 census earlier.

But why were the seats frozen as per 1971 census? And why it has become a topic of debate in the present context needs to be understood. Another point that has to be equally noted is can this new exercise go against the federal principle, giving advantage to certain states over others?

Since Democracy is based on a broader principle of ‘One citizen, one vote, one value’ the number of seats in the Lok Sabha was allotted based on 1951, 1961 and 1971 census, (494, 522 and 543) where the population of was 36.1, 43.9 and 54.8 crore respectively. (Rangarajan R, Feb 2024) However, the entire process was frozen as per 1971 census to encourage population control measures so that the states with higher population do not end up with highest number of seats. Through the 42nd amendment this process was carried out till the year 2000 and was again extended by the 84th Amendment Act till 2026. Hence, the Lok Sabha seats that are allocated are based on the population of 1971 census, which needs to be adjusted based on the first census after 2026. The entire process was postponed as the 2021 census was not conducted due to Covid 19 pandemic.

What is the challenge?

After the population control measures were initiated during the late 70s, the southern states like Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Kerala and Andhra Pradesh took pro-active measures while the northern states

like Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh and Rajasthan saw an increase which led to uneven development and unequal distribution of resources. According to Carnegie report, after delimitation, four northern states (Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, and Uttar Pradesh) would collectively gain 22 seats, while four southern states (Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Telangana, and Tamil Nadu) would lose 17 seats. "Based on our population projections, these trends will only intensify as time goes on. In 2026, for instance, Bihar and Uttar Pradesh alone stand to gain 21 seats while Kerala and Tamil Nadu would forfeit as many as 16," the report said. Which means to say that the over populated states would be benefitted while the southern states would lose their constituencies for the pro-active measures taken by them. The southern states population is growing much slower than the northern states. "Yet the financial allocation of resources (by the apolitical finance commission) is such that the northern states receive a greater share than the southern states that is based on the population of 1971". (Praveen Chakravarthy and Vivek Dehejia) Karnataka and Tamil Nadu have raised this issue off-late regarding the state's share of finances as well the GST contribution. Karnataka went to the extent of registering its protest at New Delhi, led by its Chief Minister. Such incidents show case the disparity in the allocation of funds by the Centre. If federalism is the glue that attaches the country, then there are growing signs of dissent which can further affect the functioning of the largest democracy.

What happens if the delimitation process is exercised?

Rangarajan R, a former IAS officer, in his analysis gives two options that are being discussed in the public domain with respect to revised delimitation which is based on the projected population of various states as of 2026. The first option he refers is to continue with the existing 543 seats and the second is to increase the seats to 949 with proportionate increase among the states as shown in table 1 and 2 below:

Table 1: seats retained at 543

State	No. of seats at present	Number of seats projected	Net gain/loss
U.P	80	91	11
Bihar	40	50	10
Rajasthan	25	31	6
M.P.	29	33	4
TN.	39	31	-8
Andhra+ Telengana	42	34	-8
Kerala	20	12	-8
Karnataka	28	26	-2
Punjab	13	12	-1
Himachal Pradesh	4	3	-1
Uttarakhand	5	4	-1

Table 2: seats increased to 848

State	No. of seats at present	Number of seats projected	Net gain
U.P.	80	143	63
Bihar	40	79	39
Rajasthan	25	50	25
M.P.	29	52	23
T.N.	39	49	10
Andhra + Telangana	42	54	12
Kerala	20	20	--
Karnataka	28	41	13
Punjab	13	18	5
H.P.	4	4	--
Uttarakhand	5	72	2

(Source: Based on Vaishnav et al, Carnegie endowment)

From the above tables it can be noticed that smaller states like Punjab, H.P. and Uttarakhand, as well as some northeastern states are at a disadvantaged position, which may go against the federal principle that we have adopted and may lead to a feeling of disenchantment in the population that takes away their right to representation. (Rangarajan R, Feb 2024)

The second challenge that the states face is allocation of funds that are based on several factors like population, area, fiscal capacity and fiscal discipline. The finance commission takes into cognizance the following factors while distributing financial resources to the states that have often sparked debates about regional disparity and political bias especially between the north and south states.

1. Population: 25% weightage is given to population of states
2. Area: 10% weightage given to area
3. Fiscal capacity: 47.5%
4. Fiscal discipline: 17.5%

Based on the above criteria, UP is provided with highest financial resources i.e.2,23,737.23 crore or around 18%, while Karnataka has received 6,498 crore (24-25)

The latest union budget is an example for this which has again sparked the controversy wherein states like Tamil Nadu, Kerala and Karnataka have accused the centre's bias against the southern states while allocating more funds to Bihar and Andhra Pradesh.

Karnataka's Chief Minister has called it a gross injustice by the Centre in the devolution of funds. Another prominent minister in the State cabinet has also expressed his dissatisfaction over the issue stating that "Post-independence, though Karnataka has managed effectively in implementing the population measures and enhancing educational opportunities, yet while distributing funds, the Centre has shown its inclination towards northern states that have not taken any measures to control population as well backward in education. This has affected the states representation in the Lok Sabha too.

While the delimitation might have initiated debates and discussions on the north south issues it has to be looked into from a larger perspective of safeguarding the federal structure. The need for periodically readjusting the electoral boundaries comes from the normative notion of equality of representation, according to which electoral districts ought to be delimited that they contain an equal number of voting population. (Blainski and Young, 2001) From this perspective, fair representation is ensured when citizens' votes across constituencies have equal value which we call it as a doctrine of "one person-one vote-one value". (Mohd.Sanjeer Alam, October 16, 2024)

Historically, since India has experienced uneven growth of population, demographic transition becomes essential. Anticipating this uneven growth that might disturb the principle of population parity, the framers of the constitution provided for a periodic readjustment of constituency boundaries.(ibid) However the suspension of delimitation for a very long period of time has led to the huge population disparities across states and rise in population amongst the northern states which has already been explained in the previous paragraphs. The challenge or the bottleneck here is the regional imbalance in population that has given rise to the debates and the uneven allocation of seats to Lok Sabha (as mentioned in Table 2). The five states will be at a disadvantaged position losing 24 Lok Sabha seats while the northern Hindi speaking states will have a whopping 34 seats gain.

Delimitation and gender identities:

On the one hand if delimitation process of 2026 could have a bearing on southern states, it could possibly have a negative impact on women's political participation too. Women's reservation is one of the pertinent question that arise as the central government linked the women's reservation bill 2023 to the delimitation process, which has caused a concern among many political parties. However, it has been argued by the government that delimitation may increase women's political representation which may seem to be a remote possibility as the home minister had categorically mentioned that the women's

reservation bill would be implement only after the 2029 further reducing their chances of political representation.

Conclusion:

The only suggestion that has been put forth by political scientists is that the number of seats to the Rajya Sabha has to be proportionally increased which may give appropriate representation to the states thus protecting the federal principle of the constitution. This federation is a union which is indestructible. “Though the people are divided into different states as a country, we are an one integral while, its people a single people living under a single imperium and derived from a single source.... The Constitution” Hence, despite all the issues, strengthening democracy becomes pertinent and for that the Centre-State relations should be further strengthened.

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SMART CITIES IN INDIA**Dr. Diwakar***Associate Professor & H O D, Dept of Political Science, Maharaja's College, University of Mysore
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Abstract

A city equipped with basic infrastructure to give a decent quality of life, a clean a sustainable environment through application of some smart solutions. Public information, grievance redressal, electronic service delivery, citizens' engagement, waste to energy & fuel, waste to compost, 100% treatment of waste water, smart meters & management, monitoring water quality, renewable source of energy, efficient energy and green building, smart parking, intelligent traffic management system. Smarter City use digital technology and information and communication technologies (ICT) to better quality and performance this engage more effectively and actively with its citizen. A developed urban area that creates sustainable economic development and high quality of life by excelling in multiple key areas; economy, mobility, environment, people, living, and government. Excelling in these key areas can be done so through strong human capital, social capital, and or ICT infrastructure. The smarter city applications are major goal of improving the management and transforming the urban areas. The major technological, economic and environmental changes have generated interest in smart cities. Smart cities lead to sustainable development.

Key words: *Infrastructure, Smart city and Sustainable Development*

Introduction

India launched its National Smart Cities Mission (SCM) in 2015 with the goal of transforming urban areas into more inclusive, sustainable environments. The program was a response to the needs of a rapidly urbanizing population which requires a radical transformation of the built environment in order to realize a more prosperous and egalitarian society.

A city equipped with basic infrastructure to give a decent quality of life, a clean a sustainable environment through application of some smart solutions. Public information, grievance redressal, electronic service delivery, citizens' engagement, waste to energy & fuel, waste to compost, 100% treatment of waste water, smart meters & management, monitoring water quality, renewable source of energy, efficient energy and green building, smart parking, intelligent traffic management system.

Objectives of the study:

- 1.To find out Smart city and Sustainable development
- 2.. To find out the implementation of National smart cities Mission
3. To find out the role of the Government.

Methodology**1.Based on secondary data**

The smart city mission aims to enhance the quality of life in 120 selected cities by providing efficient services, robust infrastructure, and a sustainable environment. Through smart solutions, the mission seeks to promote economic growth, inclusivity, and sustainability by focusing on the social, economic, physical, and institutional pillars of urban development. By addressing residents' diverse needs— from housing and transport to education, healthcare, and recreation—the mission aspires to create dynamic urban spaces that evolve to meet the aspirins of their citizens, serving as replicable models for other cities.

Approach of the Mission

Implementing the Smart City Mission is carried out primarily through two approaches. First, under the Smart Cities Mission, cities are being developed using an Area-Based Development (ABD) approach, where each of the 100 cities has selected a defined area for targeted interventions. These ABD areas, chosen through citizen participation, are being developed as replicable models for other parts of the city.

Second, every city has included Pan-City Projects, which are technology-driven solutions. Other key dimensions of the mission include creating a Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) structure for program implementation, promoting multiple sources of funding for projects, fostering competitive federalism, and engaging citizens.

Progress under the Mission

More than 8,000 multi-sectoral projects are being developed by these 100 cities, amounting to approximately ₹1.6 lakh crore. More than 90% of the total projects (7,244 projects amounting to ₹1,45,312 crore) undertaken under the Smart Cities Mission have been completed. Each city has developed a diverse set of projects, many of which are unique and being implemented for the first time, thus enhancing the cities' capabilities and experience and achieving broader transformational goals at the city level. 75% of projects have been completed in 75 smart cities. Across the 100 cities to date, seventeen (17) cities have completed 100% of their projects under the mission. This is followed by thirty-four (34) cities with more than 90% of projects completed and another twenty-four (24) cities with more than 75% of projects completed. On the financial front, the total outlay of Central assistance for the Smart Cities Mission was ₹48,000 crore. The Central Government has already released ₹46,787 crore to 100 Smart Cities under the SCM, of which over 90% has been utilized.

Major Projects Under the Smart City Mission Key Achievements of the Mission Integrated Command and Control Centers (ICCC): All 100 Smart Cities have operational ICCCs, which utilize data for making informed decisions. These ICCCs functioned as COVID war rooms during the pandemic and have significantly improved city operations such as transport, water supply, and solid waste management by integrating emerging technologies like AI, IoT, and Data Analytics.

Public Safety and Security: Over 83,000 CCTV surveillance cameras have been installed in 120 Smart Cities, aiding in crime monitoring. Additionally, 1,884 emergency call boxes, 3,000 public address systems, and traffic enforcement systems for red light violations and automatic number plate recognition have been installed, enhancing public safety.

Water Supply: More than 9,900 kilometers of the water supply system are being monitored through SCADA, reducing non-revenue water and leakages. **Solid Waste Management:** Over 50 cities are managing solid waste with increased technology use, improving route management, efficiency of collection, and daily management. Around 4,400 vehicles have been RFID-enabled for Automatic Vehicle Location (AVL) to digitize and improve solid waste management efficiency. **Streetlights:** More than 52 lakh solar/LED streetlights have been installed, and over 86,000 kilometers of underground electricity cabling have been constructed.

Mobility: Over 4,700 kilometers of smart roads have been constructed or improved, and 580 kilometers of cycle tracks have been developed. Furthermore, an Intelligent Transport Management System (ITMS) has been implemented and is being monitored through ICCCs, improving traffic operations, enforcing traffic violations, and reducing journey time.

Affordable Housing and Shelter: 49,300 dwelling units have been constructed, along with 1,562 rooms in community housing projects such as Rain Basera, hostels (noneducational), and night shelters under

the Mission. Vibrant Public Spaces: Over 1,300 parks, green spaces, and lakefront/riverfront promenades have been developed or are under development. Education: 7,654 smart classrooms and 40 digital libraries have been developed. Health: 172 e-health centers and clinics (without dedicated beds) have been developed, and 155 health ATMs also have been installed. Economic Hubs: 21 incubation centers/skill development centers have been developed, and over 56 market redevelopment projects have been completed. PPP: More than 50 cities have successfully developed or are developing 199 projects through Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) worth ₹9,200 crore.

The Mission has continually adapted to emerging needs, providing cities with the flexibility to respond effectively. For example, when the COVID-19 pandemic raised global awareness about the importance of open spaces for active and healthy lifestyles, the Mission launched campaigns such as India 'Cycles4Change' and 'Streets4People' in a challenge format. To ensure that even the most vulnerable citizens have access to public spaces, especially young children and caregivers, cities participated in 'Placemaking Marathons' and the 'Nurturing Neighborhoods Challenge'. Other challenges like 'Transport4All' and 'Eat Smart Cities' are promoting startups in public transport and improving food hygiene in smart cities, respectively.

Only 10% of the remaining projects are at the implementation stage. Some of these projects have been delayed due to legal issues, delays in obtaining clearances from different departments, land acquisition challenges, construction in hilly areas, and challenges in vendor and resource availability in small and medium cities. Following multiple requests from State governments and Members of Parliament, the mission period has been extended to 31st March 2025 to complete the ongoing projects.

Strategy for Smart Cities Mission

The Smart Cities Mission aims to drive economic growth and improve the quality of life by fostering local area development and leveraging technology for smart outcomes. The strategy includes transforming existing areas (through retrofitting and redevelopment), developing new areas (greenfield development), and applying smart solutions city-wide (Pan-city initiatives).

Retrofitting involves enhancing a built-up area (over 500 acres) to make it more efficient and livable by introducing intensive infrastructure and smart applications, often completed in a shorter timeframe for replication. Redevelopment replaces existing structures to create a new layout with improved infrastructure, mixed land use, and increased density, typically in areas over 50 acres. Notable examples include the Saifee Burhani Upliftment Project in Mumbai and the redevelopment of East Kidwai Nagar in New Delhi. Greenfield Development introduces smart solutions in previously undeveloped areas (over 250 acres) with innovative planning and affordable housing, addressing the needs of expanding urban populations. The GIFT City in Gujarat is a prime example.

Pan-city Development applies selected smart solutions to enhance existing city-wide infrastructure. For instance, intelligent traffic management systems can reduce commute times, while smart metering and wastewater recycling can improve water management. Each city's Smart City proposal should include one of the area-based models (retrofitting, redevelopment, or greenfield development) and a Pan-city feature, ensuring inclusivity and benefits for all residents. For North Eastern and Himalayan states, the development area requirements are halved.

Smarter City use digital technology and information and communication technologies (ICT) to better quality and performance this engage more effectively and actively with its citizen. A developed urban area that creates sustainable economic development and high quality of life by excelling in multiple key areas; economy, mobility, environment, people, living, and government. Excelling in these key areas can be done so through strong human capital, social capital, and or ICT infrastructure. Definitions The

term "smart cities" is a bit ambiguous. Some people choose a narrow definition That is cities that use information and communication technologies to deliver services to their citizens. Some people are a broader definition: Smart cities use Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) to be more intelligent and efficient in the use of resources, resulting in cost and energy savings, improved service delivery and quality of life, and reduced environmental footprint - all supporting innovation and the low carbon economy. A city that monitors and integrates conditions of all of its critical infrastructures, including roads, bridges, tunnels, rails, subways, airports, seaports, communications, water, power, even major buildings, can better optimize its resources, plan its preventive maintenance activities, and monitor security aspects while maximizing services to its citizens.

The 100 Smart Cities Mission in India was launched by Prime Minister Narendra Modi on June 25, 2015, project that aims to drive economic growth and improve the lives of urban citizens across the country by enabling local area development and harnessing smart technology, that is the vision and mission of the Prime Minister of India. The IBM is the company that originally coined the term "smart city." With their Smarter City Challenge programme, the company has developed their vision of urbanization – based on centralization of data, with a strong focus on security – across the world. The smarter city applications are major goal of improving the management and transforming the urban areas. The major technological, economic and environmental changes have generated interest in smart cities. Smart cities lead to sustainable development. It is a city where there is a significant and extensive improvement in the physical, social and economic infrastructure.

THE IMPORTANT FEATURES OF SMART CITY MISSION IN INDIA

Smart Cities Mission, which is to drive economic growth and improve the quality of life.

- It promotes mixed land use as per the area. With the mission, the states will have more flexibility to use the land for various purposes and make bye-laws as per the change. However, fulfillment of environmental safeguards will be taken care of.
- It aims to expand housing opportunities for everyone. Housing is one of the essential requirements for the growth of the Smart Cities Mission. Smart cities require more housing projects to cater to large and lower-income demographics.
- Smart Cities Mission visions to reduce congestion, ensure security, reduce air pollution and promote interaction and local economy. New way pedestrians are built for walkers and cyclists to reduce accidents.
- Development of playgrounds, parks, open gyms and other recreational spaces is another objective. This is done to enhance the quality of life for Indian citizens.
- More transport options are promoted, like transit-oriented development (TOD) and public transport.
- To bring transparency and accountability in governance, more online services are launched. For example, a citizen can use an online website instead of going to the municipal offices.
- Identity is provided to the city based on the education sector, health sector, local cuisine, sports, culture, art, furniture etc.
- Smart Solutions are applied to infrastructure and services for area development.

SMART SOLUTION OF SMART CITIES MISSION

Under the mission smart solutions are being used for the basic infrastructure like: -

1. Public information and grievance redressal
2. Electronic service delivery
3. Citizens-city's eye and ear

4. Video crime monitoring
5. Citizen engagement
6. Waste to compost
7. Waste to energy and fuel
8. Every drop to be treated
9. Treatment of C&D waste
10. Smart meters and management for water and electricity

List of 110 Cities Selected under Smart City Mission

Name of State/UT	Names of Selected Cities
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	1. Port Blair
Andhra Pradesh	1. Vishakhapatnam
	2. Tirupati
	3. Kakinada
	4. Amaravati
Arunachal Pradesh	1. Pasighat
Assam	1. Guwahati
Bihar	1. Muzaffarpur
	2. Bhagalpur
	3. Biharsharif
	4. Patna
Chandigarh	1. Chandigarh
Chhattisgarh	1. Raipur
	2. Bilaspur
	3. Naya Raipur
Daman & Diu	1. Diu
Dadra & Nagar Haveli	1. Silvassa
Delhi	1. New Delhi Municipal Council
Goa	1. Panaji
Gujarat	1. Gandhinagar
	2. Ahmedabad
	3. Surat
	4. Vadodara
	5. Rajkot
	6. Dahod
Haryana	1. Karnal
	2. Faridabad
Himachal Pradesh	1. Dharamshala
	2. Shimla

Jammu and Kashmir	1. Srinagar
	2. Jammu
Jharkhand	1. Ranchi
Karnataka	1. Mangalore
	2. Belagavi
	3. Shivamogga
	4. Hubli-Dharwar
	5. Tumakuru
	6. Davanegere
	7. Bengaluru
Kerala	1. Kochi
	2. Trivendrum
Lakshadweep	1. Kavaratti
Madhya Pradesh	1. Bhopal
	2. Indore
	3. Jabalpur
	4. Gwalior
	5. Sagar
	6. Satna
	7. Ujjain
Maharashtra	1. Navi Mumbai
	2. Nashik
	3. Thane
	4. Greater Mumbai
	5. Amravati
	6. Solapur
	7. Nagpur
	8. Kalyan-Dombivali
	9. Aurangabad
	10. Pune
	11. Pimpri chinchwad
Manipur	1. Imphal
Meghalaya	1. Shillong
Mizoram	1. Aizawl
Nagaland	1. Kohima
Odisha	1. Bhubaneshwar
	2. Raurkela
Puducherry	1. Oulgaret

	2. Puducherry
Punjab	1. Ludhiana
	2. Jalandhar
	3. Amritsar
Rajasthan	1. Jaipur
	2. Udaipur
	3. Kota
	4. Ajmer
Sikkim	1. Namchi
	2. Gangtok
Tamil Nadu	1. Tiruchirapalli
	2. Tirunelveli
	3. Dindigul,
	4. Thanjavur,
	5. Tirupur,
	6. Salem,
	7. Vellore,
	8. Coimbatore,
	9. Madurai,
	10. Erode,
	11. Thoothukudi
	12. Chennai
Telangana	1. Greater Hyderabad
	2. Greater Warangal
	3. Karimnagar
Tripura	1. Agartala
Uttar Pradesh	1. Moradabad
	2. Aligarh
	3. Saharanpur
	4. Bareilly
	5. Jhansi
	6. Kanpur
	7. Allahabad
	8. Lucknow
	9. Varanasi
	10. Ghaziabad
	11. Agra
	12. Rampur

Uttarakhand	1. Dehradun
West Bengal	1. New Town Kolkata
	2. Bidhannagar
	3. Durgapur
	4. Haldia

A total of 120 cities are selected as of date. In the first slot, West Bengal, Mumbai and Navi Mumbai submitted the proposal, but later, they withdrew the application. Most of the cities are from Uttar Pradesh and Tamil Nadu in the Smart Cities Mission.

SMART CITY A PROBABLE SOLUTION

Cities are real time systems and deem to be supermodels of efficiency, friendliness and preparedness on a mass scale but as the populations swell inexorably due to migration and other factors leading to formation of urban agglomerations from cities, they need to navigate their challenges of growing demand for new constituent services by identifying potential solutions for ever increasing complicated problems within the constrained budgets, often resulting into proliferation of point solutions: emergency response integration, traffic congestion alleviation, waste and water management, smart buildings, smart grids, etc. The cities need to equip themselves to integrate these point solutions to cater to the increasing demands placed on them, rather than crumbling under the growing demand and pressure. The "smart city" has become a buzzword over last few years in the realm of government/administration, marketing giants/investors, academia/urban research laboratories and the common mass or the end users. Almost everyone has their own comprehension and conception of Smart City i.e. "what should it be?" and "how should it be?" etc. The smart city projects (i.e. development of new towns or transformation of old cities) that are currently going on or have completed (like Amsterdam, Seoul, etc.) have different set of parameters and characteristics to address different priorities and problems and to call themselves SMART. In the absence of any clear cut or globally accepted definition of Smart City, various attempts have been made to define, categorize and integrate the parameters of smart cities as different subsystems of the urban system. One such categorization has been done by Chourabi et. al. as eight critical factors of management and organization, technology, governance, policy context, people and communities, economy, built infrastructure, and natural environment besides some others, and the major classification include some or all of these in one way or the other. Some of the green field development in the name of sustainable and smart cities have also been conceptualized and developed in India as Lavasa, Gift City (Ahmedabad), Kochi Smart City, Nano City besides some other like Dholera being labelled as Smart Cities. But there are far from satisfactory in terms of numbers and scale to meet the pace of urbanization and demand in the country, and is an urgent need of brown field development in this regard.

THE NEED FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMART CITIES

1. Smart cities are needed to bring in growth and development in a country.
2. Smart cities are needed for the development of the quality of life of people in the cities.
3. If the quality of life of the people is improved in cities, then naturally the city will attract more people and thereby more investments.

The Smart Cities Mission - Government of India, launched 100 smart cities missions in 2015. The objective is to integrate city functions; utilize scarce resources more efficiently and overall improve the quality of life of citizens. To improve safety and security to improve the efficiencies of municipal services. Use of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) is at the core of

enhancing the city's live ability, workability, and sustainability. The Ministry of Urban Development has identified 24 key areas that cities must address in their 'smart cities' plan. Of these 24 key areas, 3 are directly related to water and 7 are indirectly related to water Smart-meter management, leakage identification, preventive maintenance and water quality modelling. Smart Cities Mission is one of the mechanisms that will help operationalize the nationwide implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) priorities like poverty alleviation, employment and other basic services. Smart Cities Mission - Planning Initially, there was a lack of clarity as there was no universal definition of a smart city. The Government of India did not prescribe any particular model as they realized one size did not fit all, from the experiences of previous Urban Development Missions. Every city had to formulate its own concept, vision, mission and plan which is appropriate to its local context, resources and level of ambition.

DIMENSIONS

Cities development presently depends not only on the city's endowment of hard infrastructure (Physical Capital) and social infrastructure (Intellectual and Social Capital) but also on the availability and quality of ICTs (Information and Communication Technologies). The ICT Form of capital is decisive for urban competitiveness. Based on this background the concept of the "smart city" has been introduced as a strategic device to encompass modern urban production factors in a common framework. Smart Cities outlines many of the opportunities for cities afforded by these contemporary technologies, indicating how the 'smart city' approach might fundamentally transform the way that cities are governed, operated, interacted with and experienced. Smart Cities can be identified along six main dimensions

These axes are

- Smart Economy - Innovation and Competitiveness
- Smart Mobility- Transport and Infrastructure
- Smart Environment - Sustainability and Resources
- Smart People - Creativity and Social Capital
- Smart Living - Quality of Life and Culture
- Smart Governance - Empowerment and Participation

TECHNOLOGICAL AGENTS

The most profound technologies are those that disappear. They weave themselves into the fabric of everyday life until they are indistinguishable from it, Digital technologies captures, stores, analyses, manages, and presents data that is linked to a particular location and helps in resource management, asset management, archaeology, environmental impact assessment and urban planning.

These digital technologies introduced in the very fabric of the city space is inflicting fundamental changes on the connection between the city and its inhabitants. At the same time, it is making the hidden layers of social, economic, political processes and environmental, tensions, and flows transparent and visible in ways that were never possible before. Cities are made up of huge networks of people, organizations, businesses, infrastructure, consumption, energy, spaces and last but not least with technologies.

In a Smart City, these networks are linked together, supporting and feeding off each other. The process of linking the many different networks of the city together in a system presents a number of technological as well as governance-related and social challenges.

Starting with the technological challenges, most of the solutions which are needed in a Smart City have already been developed Solar panels, smart home appliances, electric vehicles, wind turbines, smart grids, building management systems etc. all have the potential to become part of the Smart City.

Being a smart technology, however, is not just about using less energy or being made of smart and reusable materials. It is about being able to function as an integral part of a larger system.

GATHER DATA

Smart City technology means being able to constantly gather information about the city which can be used by the technology itself in order to adapt to the most sustainable and smart behavior. An Ex. of this is a Smart Building System, which constantly gathers data about performance of a building, which it then uses to optimize energy use.

COMMUNICATE DATA

It should also be able to share that data with people or things (Objects) or other technologies or borrow relevant data from elsewhere. In this sense, smart technology should be able to communicate with the rest of a Smart City system. For this to be the case, it needs to be able 'speak the same language' as the other devices in the Smart City system. Furthermore, it needs to be connected to a common communicative platform where information can be shared and interoperability can be promoted.

MULTI-FUNCTIONAL

Although technology which is able to gather data and communicate with other technologies is indeed smart, truly smart technologies are multi-functional. This means that they provide solutions to multiple problems. One Ex. could be the electric vehicle. This not only leads to less congestion; in connection with a smart grid, it can also serve as an energy buffer, which would help level out the energy supply and demand curve. Cities are adopting smart technologies for different reasons: Amsterdam to reduce its carbon emissions, Tokyo to become more competitive, and China to tackle its resource scarcity. Elsewhere, South Korea is using cities like living labs to help domestic companies drive growth in other markets, specifically in India and China. In every case, the smart city is the beginning of initiatives that will drive big changes on the earth over several decades. "The city is a relatively manageable entity when compared to the earth. Smart cities use Internet of Things (IoT) technologies to be more intelligent and efficient in the use of resources, resulting in cost and energy savings, improved service delivery and quality of life, and reduced environmental footprint-all supporting innovation and the low-carbon economy. The main advantages of creation of smart cities

are Smart Grid, Prevent Fires, Digital Governance, Waste Management, Water Management, Surveillance Security, Land – Use Planning Changes, Intelligence Transportation, Regional Green Cities, Quality of Urban Citizen Life Improvement, Smarter places to Visit, Live, Work and Play, Sustainable Development through Innovation Cities and finally which leads to for the nation's Economic Growth.

THE STATE OF ART

According to IBM's report from the IBM Institute for Business Value, "A Vision of Smarter Cities", in the next 20 years, for every minute, on an average 30 Indians will migrate from rural areas to smarter cities for their livelihood. So as per this prediction, India needs to create 500 new cities in the forthcoming 20 years. In addition to this according to a study by consulting firm of Booz & Company also an average of 30 people will move from rural areas to the city for every minute in India, so the country is set to build 500 new cities over the next 20 years to house 700 million more city dwellers by 2050,

Establishing two smart cities in each of India's 28 states in the country under phase II of the Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Renewal Mission (JNNURM): that is the goal of the wide-range in project introduced by the Indian government to inject smart technology into cities home to between 500,000 and one million people an ambition that goes hand in hand with seven other smart- city projects already underway. The smart cities project is not meant for metropolitan cities. It is for smaller cities with half a million to one million population cities like Ujjain, and Jabalpur, as officially cited. Bigger cities are already covered under other schemes.

According to 2011 census, about 32% of India's population lives in urban areas. It is projected to grow and reach 40% in a decade and 50% in about 30 years. The JNNURM was launched in 2005 by the Government of India to last for a period of seven years.

Upgrading social and economic infrastructure in cities, provision of basic services to urban poor, introducing reforms to strengthen municipal governance are the principal strategies adopted in this JNNURM mission. The aim of the Mission is to encourage reforms and fast-track planned development of identified cities. The Mission also focuses on inclusive growth of cities with safe drinking water, improved public transport, sustainable environment, and standardized service level. Community participation in urban local bodies is also part of the mission. One of the basic reasons for investments flocking in to the smaller cities is available properties and affordable prices. Moreover, the special initiatives taken by the respective governments in providing the smaller cities with infrastructural facilities and creation of SEZs, has played a vital role in promoting these small towns into cities of the future. Keeping in view all the congenial factors necessary for setting up corporate infrastructure, the investing companies ranging from pharmaceuticals to financial institutions, automobiles to the IT & ITES (IT-Enabled Services) sectors; to the retail and real estate sector are opting for the smaller cities transforming them into India's fastest growing cities in a matter.

GIFT (Gujarat International Finance Tec-City)

Designed as modern recreation of India's architectural past, mirrored twins of the Gateway. It will house over a million people with millions more commuting there daily. Well placed between the political and commercial capitals of Gujarat. GIFT is a public-private partnership, it will India's first major super tall Central Business District project that is designed to be the focal point of both the world's and India's booming financial services market by providing companies with all those things Mumbai is still developing: comprehensive infrastructure, power, virtualized office space, a well-designed, planned & expandable urban form.

KOCHI

Smart City Kochi is an IT Special Economic Zone under construction in Kochi, Kerala Smart City (Kochi) Infrastructure Pvt. Ltd. is a joint venture company formed to develop the Kochi Smart City project. Government of Kerala (16% share), TECOM Investments (84% share), a subsidiary of Dubai Holding are the main investors of the company. "The four-storeyed building project of 22 lakh sq. ft. spread over 50 acres will be located on the banks of Kadambra at Edachira near Kakkanad.

BANGALORE

Bangalore is going to be a Smarter City through an Indo-German-Research Project mainly, Smart Mobility including (Noise, Pollutants); (E-Mobility, Car Sharing); (Information, Traffic Management); (Walkability, Distances, Modal Split); (High Occupation Rate); (Smart PT, Linkage with Private); (Safety, Accessibility, Costs); (Energy Efficiency). The Government of Karnataka has inked an agreement with networking solution provider Cisco for a pilot programme to develop the roadmap for an intelligent, smart and sustainable Bangalore city. The pilot programme would aim at developing replicable ICT solutions to help promote sustainable, intelligent urban development practices in the city. The company also unveiled its blueprint for "Intelligent Urbanization," a global initiative to help cities around the world use the network as the next utility for integrated city.

FINANCING OF SMART CITY MISSION IN INDIA

In total, the government has funded a sum of Rs 7,20,000 crore. On average Rs 100 crore per city over the five years. The scheme will be operated as a Centrally Sponsored Scheme (CSS) on a 50:50 model, meaning Rs 50 crore will be contributed by the center and Rs 50 crore by the state government or Union Territories. This has also become one of the challenges for India's smart city mission because, until November 2021, the Center government released Rs 27,282 crore, whereas states have released only Rs 20,124 crore.

Smart Cities Mission - Implementation

Established SPV (Special Purpose Vehicle) in each city for

1. Decision making
2. Planning
3. Project designing and
4. Implementation.

Smart Cities Mission - Progress/Achievements

1. Creation of smart command and control centers in 17 cities - this has integrated different service networks and the city administration can centrally monitor and it gives an impetus to decision making.
2. Smart Roads - 60 projects completed in 25 cities.
3. Smart Solar Projects - 27 projects completed in 17 cities
4. Smart Waste Water Projects - 12 projects completed in 10 cities
5. Smart Water Projects - 38 projects completed in 24 cities

Notable Progress in Bhopal Smart City Project

1. Establishment of Integrated Command and Control Centre - to increase the safety and security of its people.
2. Establishment of Cloud-based disaster recovery center.

Smart Cities Mission - Challenges

- 3.. A lot of progress is desired in creating energy-efficient and green buildings.
4. Making Urban Bodies self-reliant

5.. Share of public transport is declining; it needs to be increased to meet the needs of increasing urbanization.

6. Rising air pollution, increase in road congestion due to increase in urbanization

OTHER MISSIONS RELATED TO SMART CITIES MISSION

To make the mission successful, other government-initiated projects are interlinked. Overall development can occur by integrating the social, economic, physical, and institutional infrastructure. A great benefit can be achieved by the convergence of sectoral schemes

- AMRUT- Atal Mission for Rejuvenation and Urban Transformation
- HRIDAY- Heritage City Development and Augmentation Yojana
- Make in India
- Digital India
- Swach Bharat Abhiyan
- Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR SMART CITIES MISSION

There are a few recommendations that can help achieve more significant benefits from the mission

- It should be a long-term programme, not only a five-year programme as most of the cities cannot perform the best within this time frame.
- To meet the city requirement, more projects should be identified. There are many smart cities whose drainage issue is not yet solved.
- Studies should be done on why a single project has not been completed in cities like Amaravati, Bhagalpur, Muzaffarpur and Shillong.
- For the mobilization of funds, more revenue should be generated through taxation. The fund transfer process should also be made accessible.
- All these cities should be secured by cyber security- ensuring data security and encryption.

CHALLENGES OF SMART CITIES

The following are the challenges of smart cities in India

1. Most of the ingredients needed for the urban transformation exist, their full potential remains underutilized.
2. There is negligence in monitoring the progress of development schemes and in the upkeep of public places.
3. Sufficient efforts are not being made to understand the working conditions of functionaries (i.e., local government officials and elected representatives) and their grievances.
4. Governance practices are influenced by numerous internal and external forces. In other words, due to vested interests, civic officials and elected representatives do not perform their duties efficiently and at times indulge in corrupt practices.
5. When citizens see a management and governance deficit, many of them operate in an irresponsible manner.
6. The Ministry of Urban Development used a competition method based on an area-based-development strategy to select the cities for the mission.
7. At first, cities competed at a state level, and then the winner competed on a national level Smart City Challenge. The cities that scored the highest marks were selected as Smart City. The nominations came from the state government.

CONCLUSION

The smart city concept is one such upcoming concept which is deemed to be the solution for the present-day problems as well as the sustainable future. Smart cities are the modern urban concepts that are essential for people to have quality life. It is the conceptual view of grouping various technologies to attain smart and sustainable practices. But in the absence of any definite guidelines and case specific solutions to develop the smart cities in India, there is need for further research to work out the parameters, definitions and guidelines for the development of new cities on green field as well as the brown field developments.

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EDUCATIONAL INITIATIVES FOR DEMOCRATIC AWARENESS HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM IN INDIA

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Abstract

Education is a systematic process to acquire knowledge, experience, skills and social attitudes. Effective and expected implementation of education includes creation of educational environment, awareness towards social problems; focus on the professional ethics and human values, etc., education wants to increase morality and intellectual level of students. A developed nation is invisibly. India need well skilled and highly educated people who can drive our economy forward.

Keywords: *Knowledge, Skill, Institution, Population, Challenges, University*

Introduction

India is the second largest higher education system in the World and the third largest pool of skilled man power. As per 2011 census, about 8.15% of Indians are Graduates, with Union Territories of Chandigarh and Delhi topping the list with 24.65% and 24.65% of their population being graduates respectively. The higher education system in India has grown in a remarkable way, particularly in the post-independence period. In 2023, there were more than 1,114 universities, with a break up of 56 central universities, 460 state universities, 128 deemed universities, 430 private universities, 4 institute under state legislature Act, and 171 institutes of National Importance which include 21 IIMS, 20 AIIMS, 23 IITs, 25 IIITs, 7 IISERs and 31 NITs among others. And 58,000 colleges catering to more than 73 million students spread across every state and union territory. Higher education promotes quality learning as a consequence of both teaching and research and is essential for the emerging knowledge society in general and knowledge economy in particular. Hence, government is mainly responsible for providing higher education accessible to all. However, the higher education system in India is facing several challenges. The challenge of global competitiveness has been added to other demanding tasks such as, equity, relevance, quality, and access to all in the face of a resource crisis. Increasing in the Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) and also improving the quality of higher education has been the crux of the issue. Institutional reforms with regard to structural and functional aspects are instrumental in changing the higher education system.

Knowledge is Power and hence, Education in general and higher education in particular is one of the basic requirements and driving force for appropriate utilization of the human resource available in the nation for nation building which is true for all nations and even more true for the developing countries like India. India's great Educationist and President, Dr. S. Radhakrishnan rightly pointed out, "*democracy only provides that all men should have equal opportunities for the development of their unequal talents*", and education is the only means through which people can develop their skills and talents. Education is also an essential tool to establish an egalitarian society based on social equality and social justice.

For any society, to achieve exponential growth, it is essential to gear up skill based activities through a potential, vibrant and dynamic educational system. The present scenario of the higher education in India reveals the fact that it is suffering from both quantitative and qualitative set back. There is dearth of Higher Educational Institutions to absorb the out coming student population from

secondary level to college / Under-Graduate system. Apart from quantity, quality maintenance, enhancement and management have been great threat and challenge too.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the educational initiatives for democratic awareness in India.
2. To identify the basic challenges of higher educational system in the country.

The higher education system in India has grown in a remarkable way particularly in the post-independence period, to become one of the largest systems of the world. The higher education system has many issues of concern at present like financing, management, access, quality and relevance, reorientation of programmes health consciousness, values, ethics and quality of higher education. The higher education in 21st century will be significantly different from what it was in the 20th century and therefore, there is urgent need to plan for the coming years. UNESCO's policy paper on "*Change and Development of Higher Education* says",- Higher education investments are important for economic growth as they increase individuals productivity and incomes as indicated by rate of return analysis, and they also produce significant external benefits not captured by such analysis.

In the post-independent scenario, providing education to all has been prioritized in the light of development and nation building process. However, after the establishment of NAAC there has been a paradigm shift in the qualitative aspects of higher education system in the country. In the present millennium the field of higher education has underwent tremendous changes. The higher education sector in India is facing challenges and is in the plight of fundamental changes in structural and functional dimensions. Still we are facing lot of problems and challenges in our education system. Basic challenges as follow:-

1. **Enrolment** ;- GER of India in higher education is only 15% which is quite low as compared to the developed as well as ,other developing countries with the increase of enrolments at school.
2. **Quality** ;-Quality in higher education is a multidimensional, multilevel ,and dynamic concept .Ensuring quality in higher education,- is amongst the foremost challenges being faced in India today.
3. **Faculty**:-Faculty shortages and the inability of the state educational system to attract and retain well qualified teachers have been posing challenges to quality education for many years. Large numbers of NET/SLET/ Ph,D candidates are unemployed even there are lot of vacancies in higher education.
4. **Research and innovation**;- There are very nominal scholars in our country whose writings cited by famous western authors. There inadequate focus on research in higher education institutes. There are insufficient resources and facilities.
5. **Political interference**;- Most of the educational institutions are owned by the political leaders, who are playing role in governing council member of the universities. They are using the innocent students for their selfish means.

The new challenge before the country at the beginning of the 21st century is to become a developed society by the year 2024. With the exclusive growth of knowledge in the past century and the development of handy tools of information and communication technologies as well as other scientific innovations, competition has become a hallmark all over the world. During the last 50 years higher education in India has made great strides leading the Indian higher education to become one of the largest systems in the world. But the Indian higher education system is complex because of a variety of factors, administration, political financial and parochial. To be efficient and internationally

competitive, it has to resolve many issues and for a proper appreciation of these issues, it is necessary to be conversant with the basic facts of Indian higher education.

Higher education system, especially in developing countries is undergoing radical changes in recent times to ensure both quality and social responsibility. The challenges are manifold. In the backdrop of globalization, achieving the goal of excellence at various spheres like student performance and competitiveness, faculty qualification and promotion of research seems to be the toughest challenge. Thus in order to improve the higher education sector both quantitatively and qualitatively, the Higher Educational Institutions should become competent enough to create such students who would efficiently meet the global challenges and standards and emerge successful in the global race. Given the crisis of moral values, ethics, social responsibility, human values, and such other among the younger generations, there is need for quality education at higher levels in the country. It is important to note that at global level only our IITs and MU gain recognition once in a way whereas, other Universities and Institutions across the country are placed at the bottom of the pyramid well within the dark corner at global level.

The major components of equality of education can be elucidated as follows:-

Competition: Competition among educational institutions for students and funds will be highly significant. In order to survive in such a situation, educational institutions need to worry about their quality.

Customer Satisfaction: Students, parents or sponsoring agencies as customers of the educational institutions are now highly conscious of their rights or getting value for their money and time spent.

Maintaining Standards: As educational institutions, we are always concerned about setting our own standards and maintaining it continuously year after year and in order to maintain the standard, we should consciously make efforts to improve quality of education.

Accountability: Every institution is accountable to its stakeholders in terms of the funds either public or private.

Improve Employee Morale And Motivation: Concern for quality as an institution will improve the morale and motivation of the staff in performing their duties and responsibilities. **Credibility Prestige and Status:** Quality will bring in credibility to individuals and institution because of consistency leading to prestige, status and brand value.

Every Indian University needs intensive attention and rigorous efforts to develop strategic management frame works that will help to enhance quality of education and prepare qualified specialists. Universities have to involve in relocation of resources that will help administrators determine which programmes and services are most efficient to achieve the mission. To restore and improve the quality of education, the University needs to follow international standards, develop different courses, upgrade of staff knowledge, familiarization with innovative aspects in the field of management and implementation of new pedagogies in knowledge distribution to the students.

Another important aspect is to establish students career centre with the help of which interface between the career interests of university graduate and the demands of the labour market and in which employment opportunities of graduates is improved. Organized career with the involvement of industry leaders and students will help create future career development and upcoming job demands.

At present, the higher education system has initiated a range of reformative measures to tread the path of success. Through my study some distinguished achievements in the last two decades can be viewed as follows:

1. India has remarkably transformed its higher education landscape by creating widespread access to low-cost high-quality university education for students of all levels.
2. With well-planned expansion and a student-centric learning-driven model of education, higher education sector has not only enhanced its enrolment numbers but has dramatically improved its learning outcomes.
3. A differentiated three-tiered university system wherein, each tier has a distinct strategic objective has enabled universities to build on their strengths and cater across different categories of educational needs.
4. With the effective use of technology, higher education system has been able to resolve the longstanding tension between excellence and equity.

Higher education has also undertaken large-scale reforms to improve faculty-student ratios by making teaching an attractive career path, expanding capacity for doctoral students at research universities and educational qualifications for teaching eligibility. Therefore Education is a systematic process to acquire knowledge, experience, skills and social attitudes.

Conclusion:

Education is a process by which a person's body, mind and character are formed and strengthened. It is bringing of head, heart and mind together and thus enabling a person to develop an all-round personality identifying the best in him or her. India being one of the leading developing countries in the World is striving hard to create a knowledge society by giving importance to higher education. Higher education institutions today need to perform various rules like creating new knowledge, acquiring new capabilities, producing intelligent human resource pool so as to meet the expectations of the society.

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INDIAN ELECTORAL SYSTEM: CURRENT CHALLENGES, REFORMS AND PATHWAYS FOR IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract

The Indian election system, one of the largest and most complex democratic processes in the world, is a testament to India's democratic spirit. However, despite its many successes, the system faces significant challenges, including political corruption, the influence of money power, and the exclusion of marginalized groups. These challenges include the influence of money and muscle power, voter disenfranchisement, and the underrepresentation of marginalized groups. This article not only explores the structural and procedural elements of the system but also incorporates a data-driven analysis to highlight key challenges. The introduction of stricter electoral finance regulations, greater transparency in party funding, implementation of technological advancements like blockchain for secure voting, and enhancing voter education programs are vital. Statistical data on voter turnout, criminalization of politics, and campaign finances are analyzed, along with proposed reforms to address these issues. Through a blend of qualitative and quantitative data, this paper provides insights into the necessary reforms to improve the democratic integrity of the Indian election system.

Key words: Indian electoral system, democracy, electoral reforms, political funding, voter education, electoral malpractices, Election Commission of India

Introduction:

India's electoral system, celebrated for its scale and procedural rigor, Over the years, the Indian electoral system has evolved into a well-established framework, with the Election Commission of India (ECI) playing a pivotal role in ensuring free and fair elections. However, with an ever-growing electorate and changing political dynamics, the system faces increasing challenges. The impact of money and muscle power, voter manipulation, and exclusion of certain groups are raising concerns about the efficacy of the democratic process. Electoral reforms have been a consistent point of debate, with the aim of ensuring transparency, accountability, and equal representation in the political system. Despite its strength, the system has faced persistent issues, from underrepresentation to the excessive influence of money and criminal elements in politics. While the Election Commission of India (ECI) has implemented several measures to ensure free and fair elections, problems persist. This paper explores these challenges using data analysis to evaluate the efficacy of the current system and to propose targeted reforms.

Meaning and Definitions: Indian Electoral System:

Indian Electoral System refers to the framework, processes, and institutions that conduct elections in India, the world's largest democracy. It is designed to allow citizens to exercise their right to vote and choose their representatives in the Parliament, state legislatures, and local bodies. **Democracy** 'A system of government in which power is vested in the people, who rule either directly or through freely elected representatives. India follows a parliamentary democratic system'. **Election** 'The formal process by which citizens choose their representatives through voting. In India, elections are held for both national (Lok Sabha) and state legislatures (Vidhan Sabha), as well as local bodies like municipalities and panchayats'. **Universal Adult Suffrage** 'Every Indian citizen aged 18 and above, irrespective of caste, religion, gender, or social status, has the right to vote'.

Objectives of the Study:

- To identify the major challenges faced by the current electoral system.
- To explore recent reforms and proposals aimed at improving electoral transparency and inclusivity.
- To analyze the structure and functioning of the Indian electoral system using available electoral data.
- To identify key challenges through the lens of data, including voter turnout rates, criminalization of politics, and campaign finance statistics.

Methodology: This study adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative analysis. Quantitative data were collected from the Election Commission of India (ECI) reports, scholarly publications, and electoral databases, including voter turnout statistics, criminal cases filed against candidates, and campaign finance reports. Qualitative data were sourced from government publications and academic research on electoral reforms.

The Indian Election System: An Overview

The Indian election system is a cornerstone of the world's largest democracy, characterized by a complex and multifaceted process that reflects the nation's diversity. Governed by the Constitution of India, the electoral framework is administered by the Election Commission of India (ECI), an autonomous body that ensures free and fair elections at both national and state levels. The Indian electoral system operates under a first-past-the-post (FPTP) system, wherein the candidate with the most votes wins, irrespective of whether they secure a majority. The ECI supervises elections at all levels, ensuring fairness through a range of administrative procedures and technological innovations, including the use of Electronic Voting Machines (EVMs) and Voter Verified Paper Audit Trails (VVPATs). However, the FPTP system has been criticized for not being fully representative, especially in a country with such a diverse electorate.

Key Features:

- ❖ Universal Adult Suffrage: Every citizen over 18 years is eligible to vote.
- ❖ Election Commission of India: A constitutional body that oversees the entire election process.
- ❖ Electronic Voting: Use of EVMs and VVPATs to ensure quick and transparent voting.
- ❖ Model Code of Conduct: Rules to regulate the conduct of political parties during elections.

Key Challenges in the Indian Electoral System:**1. Voter Turnout and Disenfranchisement.**

Voter turnout in Indian elections has varied over the years, often reflecting the engagement of different social groups and regions. A growing trend of voter apathy, particularly in urban areas, has been observed. Voter registration issues and the lack of motivation among urban voters are major contributing factors. Below is a table showcasing voter turnout data from the past three general elections.

Year	Total Voter Turnout (%)	Male Voter Turnout (%)	Female Voter Turnout (%)	Urban Turnout (%)	Rural Turnout (%)
2009	58.19%	60.1%	55.8%	49.4%	65.5%
2014	66.44%	67.09%	65.63%	56.0%	73.2%

2019	67.11%	67.5%	66.7%	59.7%	71.8%
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The steady increase in overall voter turnout from 58.19% in 2009 to 67.11% in 2019 is an encouraging sign of greater democratic participation. However, the persistent gap between urban and rural voter turnout remains a concern, as urban areas show lower engagement. This points to a growing disconnection between urban voters and the political process, often attributed to voter apathy and registration issues.

2. Muscle Power and Criminalization of Politics.

The presence of candidates with criminal backgrounds has raised serious concerns about the credibility of elected representatives. The use of intimidation and violence to influence voters, particularly in rural areas, is another persistent problem. The increasing presence of candidates with criminal records poses a severe threat to the integrity of the electoral system. According to the Association for Democratic Reforms (ADR), the number of MPs with criminal cases has risen over the years. Below is a table summarizing data from the 2014 and 2019 general elections.

Year	Total MPs Elected	MPs with Criminal Cases	Percentage of MPs with Criminal Cases	Serious Criminal Cases (%)
2014	543	186	34.3%	21.0%
2019	543	233	43.0%	29.0%

The alarming increase in MPs with criminal backgrounds, rising from 34.3% in 2014 to 43.0% in 2019, reflects the growing criminalization of politics in India. This data highlights the urgent need for electoral reforms to disqualify candidates with serious criminal charges until cleared by the judiciary.

3. Campaign Financing and the Influence of Money.

India's elections have become increasingly expensive, with political parties and candidates spending massive amounts on campaigns. The opaque system of political donations exacerbates this issue. According to a report by the Centre for Media Studies (CMS), the total expenditure in the 2019 general elections was estimated at approximately ₹60,000 crores (USD 8.5 billion), making it the costliest election in Indian history.

The increasing cost of elections is indicative of the growing influence of money power in politics. The opaque nature of political donations, despite the introduction of electoral bonds, allows for a lack of accountability in funding, necessitating reforms for transparency.

4. **Exclusion of Marginalized Groups:** Despite efforts to make the electoral process inclusive, marginalized communities, including women, Dalits, and indigenous groups, often face barriers to participation due to social and economic factors.
5. **Electoral Disinformation:** With the rise of social media, elections have become vulnerable to the spread of fake news, misinformation, and targeted propaganda, undermining the integrity of the democratic process.

Electoral Reforms: A Path Forward

- ✓ **State Funding of Elections:** To curb the influence of money in politics, state funding for political parties and candidates can be introduced. This reform aims to level the playing field and ensure that parties with fewer resources are not marginalized. As shown by the data on campaign expenditure, state funding can help level the playing field by reducing the reliance on private donations.
- ✓ **Proportional Representation (PR):** Moving from the FPTP system to PR could address concerns over unequal representation, ensuring that political power is more evenly distributed among parties.

based on the percentage of votes they receive. In the 2019 elections, the ruling party secured 37.36% of the popular vote but won 55.8% of the seats in Parliament. This disproportion suggests that PR could enhance electoral fairness.

- ✓ **Remote Voting Mechanisms:** Introducing remote voting mechanisms, especially for migrant workers and overseas citizens, can help increase voter participation and reduce disenfranchisement. According to the ECI, over 300 million eligible voters did not participate in the 2019 general elections, many due to logistical issues like migration.
- ✓ **Strengthening Anti-Defection Laws:** The existing anti-defection law needs stricter implementation to prevent political instability caused by frequent defections of elected representatives.
- ✓ **Political Transparency and Accountability:** Making political donations transparent through stringent regulatory mechanisms, like the mandatory disclosure of electoral bonds and a cap on campaign expenditures, would enhance public trust in the electoral system.
- ✓ **Stronger Regulatory Framework for Media:** With the increasing role of social media in elections, a robust regulatory framework to curb disinformation and targeted propaganda is essential for maintaining election integrity.

Recommendations of the Study:

- ✚ **Revamping Electoral Rolls & Remote Voting:** The ECI should regularly update electoral rolls to avoid the exclusion of eligible voters. Initiatives like online registration and verification must be strengthened. Implementing remote voting technologies can enhance participation, especially among migrant workers and the urban population.
- ✚ **Tackling Voter Disengagement:** Civic education campaigns aimed at increasing voter awareness, particularly in urban areas, could help reduce voter apathy. Special efforts should also be made to encourage the participation of marginalized groups.
- ✚ **Stricter Regulation on Political Funding:** The government should introduce stricter regulations on political donations and campaign finance, ensuring transparency in the use of funds.
- ✚ **Independent Media Oversight:** An independent commission should be tasked with monitoring election-related content on social media platforms to curb the spread of disinformation.
- ✚ **Criminal Justice Reforms for Politicians:** Candidates with criminal cases should be disqualified from running for office until proven innocent, to uphold the integrity of elected representatives. Amending laws to disqualify candidates with serious criminal charges until proven innocent will reduce the criminalization of politics and restore faith in the system.
- ✚ **Mandatory Disclosure of Campaign Finance:** Introducing stricter regulations for electoral bonds and mandating real-time disclosure of political donations can ensure transparency and accountability in campaign financing.
- ✚ **Strengthening the Anti-Defection Law:** Preventing defections through stricter enforcement of the anti-defection law will contribute to political stability and accountability.

Conclusion:

India's electoral system, while commendable in many respects, requires significant reforms to address its growing challenges. The rise in criminal candidates, excessive campaign expenditure, and voter disengagement are areas of immediate concern. Through state funding, proportional representation, and enhanced transparency, the system can be reformed to better represent the people. India can reinforce its democratic institutions and ensure that its electoral system evolves to meet contemporary challenges. A future pathway centered on inclusivity, transparency, and accountability

will help safeguard the core values of Indian democracy, ensuring that it remains robust and resilient. For Indian democracy to remain robust and vibrant, these reforms are essential in fostering a fair and inclusive political environment that truly represents the will of the people.

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POLITICAL INFLUENCE

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Political influence refers to the ability of individuals, groups, or organizations to shape political decisions, public opinion, and government policies. This influence can manifest through various channels, including lobbying, media, public demonstrations, and economic power. Political leaders, interest groups, and the media are primary agents of political influence, each playing distinct roles in swaying public sentiment and policymaking. Economic power, such as that held by corporations and wealthy individuals, also significantly impacts political outcomes, often through campaign contributions and lobbying efforts. Social movements and public opinion further complicate the political landscape by mobilizing citizens and creating pressure for change. This abstract examines the multiple dimensions of political influence and its role in shaping democratic and authoritarian regimes, highlighting both the positive and negative consequences of its exercise in shaping political discourse, governance, and policy.

Introduction:

Political influence is a fundamental aspect of governance and public policy-making, referring to the power individuals, groups, organizations, or even foreign entities have in shaping the decisions of governments and political leaders. It operates through various channels, such as lobbying, media, public demonstrations, and the manipulation of public opinion. In democratic societies, political influence plays a critical role in ensuring that the voices of citizens, interest groups, and political factions are heard in the policy-making process. However, it can also lead to inequalities when a small, powerful elite or corporate interests disproportionately shape policy decisions.

In authoritarian regimes, political influence can be more centralized, with power concentrated in the hands of a few. Here, influence is often exercised through control of state institutions, suppression of dissent, and the manipulation of information to maintain control over the population. Regardless of the political system, the underlying dynamics of political influence are pervasive, as it is essential in shaping public policies on a broad range of issues, from economic reform and social justice to environmental protection and foreign policy.

Review of literature:

1. Political Leaders and Elite Influence: A large body of research focuses on the role of political leaders and elites in shaping public policy. Dahl (1956) in his work *Who Governs?* examined the concentration of political power in the hands of a few elites, arguing that political decisions often reflect the interests of these elites rather than the broader population. Similarly, Mills (1956) in *The Power Elite* discussed how political, military, and corporate elites interact to control decision-making in the U.S., consolidating influence over major policy decisions. More recent scholars, such as Ziblatt (2017) in *The Politics of Resentment*, highlight how political leaders exploit public emotions and fears to secure political power and influence.

2. Interest Groups and Lobbying: Lobbying and interest group activity are pivotal to understanding political influence. A significant portion of literature focuses on how organized groups, representing economic, environmental, or social interests, influence political decisions. In *The Logic of Collective Action* (1965), Olson argued that interest groups are formed to advance specific agendas, but often their influence is disproportionate to their size due to concentrated benefits. Berman (2001) in *The Influence of Interest Groups in the U.S. Senate* examined how lobbying groups shape U.S. policy, particularly in areas like healthcare and defence spending. Lobbying remains a key area of study, with scholars exploring both its positive and negative effects on democratic processes.

3. Media and Political Influence: The role of media in political influence is another well-explored area. Media outlets, both traditional (newspapers, TV) and digital (social media), are powerful tools for shaping public opinion and influencing political outcomes. Lippmann (1922) in *Public Opinion* argued that media not only reflect the political reality but also shape it, constructing narratives that guide public perceptions. More recent scholars,

like Pariser (2011) in *The Filter Bubble*, discuss how algorithms in digital media create echo chambers that limit exposure to differing viewpoints, increasing polarization and affecting political decision-making.

4. Public Opinion and Social Movements: Public opinion has long been considered a key form of political influence, with scholars like Almond and Verba (1963) in *The Civic Culture* exploring how public attitudes towards government affect political systems. Social movements, as expressions of collective public sentiment, are seen as potent forces of change. Tilly (1978) in *From Mobilization to Revolution* theorized that social movements can shift power dynamics by directly challenging state authority. More recent research has focused on the role of social media in organizing and mobilizing movements, with examples such as the Arab Spring and Black Lives Matter demonstrating how digital platforms can amplify social movements and affect political change.

5. Economic Power and Corporate Influence: The literature also addresses the influence of economic power on politics. Research on corporate influence, campaign finance, and the “revolving door” between business and politics has raised concerns about the disproportionate power wielded by corporations and wealthy individuals in shaping policy. Gilens and Page (2014) in their study *Testing Theories of American Politics* found that economic elites and organized groups representing business interests have a far greater influence on U.S. government policy than ordinary citizens. This has led to debates about the erosion of democratic principles in favor of corporate and elite-driven policy-making.

6. Political Influence in Authoritarian Regimes: In authoritarian systems, political influence tends to be more centralized. Research by scholars such as Geddes (2003) in *Paradigms and Sand Castles* examines how political power is exercised in non-democratic regimes, where rulers maintain control through patronage, suppression of opposition, and manipulation of information. Authoritarian leaders often employ a combination of media control, surveillance, and coercion to sustain their influence and quash dissent, as noted in studies of regimes like Russia (Pomerantsev, 2014) and China (Shirk, 2007).

7. Corruption and Manipulation of Political Influence: A final strand of literature examines the negative aspects of political influence, particularly in relation to corruption. Research by Rose-Ackerman (1999) in *Corruption and Government* focuses on how political influence can lead to corruption, undermining public trust in government institutions. Corruption often occurs when individuals or groups use their influence to extract personal or financial gain at the expense of the public good, distorting democratic processes.

Objective:

The primary objective of this study is to explore and analyze the mechanisms of political influence and its impact on policy-making, governance, and societal outcomes. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Examine the key agents of political influence, including political leaders, interest groups, media, public opinion, and economic power, and how each contributes to shaping political decisions.
2. Assess the role of media and social movements in influencing public opinion and political outcomes, particularly in the context of modern digital communication platforms.
3. Investigate the impact of political influence in both democratic and authoritarian regimes, highlighting the differences in how influence is exerted and its implications on governance and policy outcomes.
4. Evaluate the positive and negative consequences of political influence, particularly in relation to issues of power imbalances, corruption, and the potential for manipulation of democratic processes.
5. Provide insights into how political influence can be balanced or regulated to ensure fair and equitable participation in the political system while reducing the risks of undue influence or exploitation.

Merits:

Political influence, when exerted ethically and responsibly, can have several positive effects on governance and society. **Some of the key merits include:**

1. **Encourages Democratic Participation:** Political influence allows various groups, organizations, and individuals to engage in the policymaking process. In democratic societies, this participation is vital for ensuring that the voices of diverse constituencies—ranging from citizens to special interest groups—are heard in the political arena. Public opinion, activism, and advocacy ensure that policies reflect the needs and desires of society.

- 2. Promotes Accountability and Transparency:** When used effectively, political influence can increase government accountability. Media, interest groups, and social movements often play a role in holding politicians and government bodies accountable for their actions, ensuring transparency and reducing corruption. Public scrutiny and pressure can push policymakers to act in the best interests of the public, enhancing democratic governance.
- 3. Facilitates Social Change:** Political influence, particularly through social movements and grassroots activism, can be a powerful tool for societal transformation. Movements for civil rights, environmental justice, gender equality, and labour rights have historically relied on political influence to challenge unjust policies and bring about legal reforms that benefit marginalized groups and promote social equity.
- 4. Enhances Policy Innovation and Progress:** Political influence helps introduce new ideas and solutions to complex problems. Interest groups, think tanks, and advocacy organizations often bring innovative research and policy proposals to the table, stimulating the policymaking process. This diversity of input can result in more dynamic, forward-thinking policies that address emerging challenges, such as climate change, technological advancements, or health crises.
- 5. Promotes Interest Representation:** Political influence enables different interest groups to advocate for policies that align with their values or needs. Whether through lobbying, public campaigns, or political contributions, these groups ensure that the interests of businesses, communities, and various sectors are considered in the policy process. This can lead to more comprehensive policies that address the diverse needs of society.
- 6. Strengthens Democratic Institutions:** A healthy exercise of political influence strengthens democratic institutions by ensuring that all segments of society, including the underrepresented and marginalized, have a say in how they are governed. This inclusivity fosters a sense of ownership and legitimacy in political systems, thereby strengthening the democratic fabric of nations.
- 7. Encourages Policy Responsiveness:** When political influence is exerted through channels like public opinion and civil society, governments are often more responsive to the changing needs of society. This responsiveness leads to more timely and effective policy adjustments, particularly during periods of crisis or transition.

Scopes:

The scope of political influence is vast, encompassing various areas where it shapes and drives political outcomes, governance, and societal change.

- 1. Policy Formation and Decision-Making:** Political influence directly impacts the creation and modification of policies. Through lobbying, advocacy, and public opinion, various interest groups and individuals can shape the legislative process, influencing the types of laws and regulations that are proposed, debated, and enacted. Political influence ensures that a wide range of issues—from economic policies to healthcare reforms—are addressed in ways that reflect the priorities of specific groups or the broader public.
- 2. Electoral Processes and Voting Behaviour:** Political influence plays a crucial role in shaping electoral outcomes. Political campaigns, media advertisements, endorsements, and party politics all use influence to sway voters' decisions. By shaping public perceptions of candidates, parties, or issues, political influence can affect voter turnout and the overall outcome of elections, thus determining the direction of political leadership and policy priorities.
- 3. Government Accountability and Transparency:** Political influence is central to holding governments accountable for their actions. Through public protests, media scrutiny, watchdog organizations, and the actions of political opposition, citizens and advocacy groups can ensure that those in power are held responsible for their decisions. This scope of influence helps to prevent corruption, promote transparency, and strengthen democratic institutions by encouraging openness and fairness in governance.
- 4. Public Opinion and Political Behaviour:** The influence of media, social movements, and public figures significantly shapes public opinion and political behaviour. Through mass media, social media platforms, and direct communication, political influence can alter public attitudes on key issues, from social justice movements

to economic policies. This, in turn, can lead to shifts in voting patterns, public attitudes toward governance, and broader societal changes.

5. Social Movements and Activism: Social movements, whether focused on civil rights, environmental protection, or gender equality, rely on political influence to advocate for change. Activists use political influence to mobilize public support, pressure lawmakers, and challenge entrenched systems of power. Movements such as the Civil Rights Movement in the United States, the anti-apartheid struggle in South Africa, and more recent climate justice movements illustrate how political influence can drive social and legal reforms.

6. International Relations and Diplomacy: Political influence extends beyond national borders, playing a critical role in shaping international relations and diplomacy. Countries use political influence through diplomatic negotiations, international alliances, foreign aid, and economic sanctions to advance their geopolitical interests. Transnational organizations, such as the United Nations or multinational corporations, also wield political influence to shape global policies on issues like trade, security, and climate change.

7. Political and Economic Systems: Political influence impacts both political and economic systems by shaping fiscal policies, regulatory frameworks, and economic reforms. The influence of business leaders, economic elites, and international financial institutions can determine economic priorities, from taxation to government spending. This scope highlights the connection between political power and economic control, with implications for wealth distribution, labor rights, and market regulations.

8. Civil Rights and Social Justice: Political influence plays a vital role in advancing civil rights and social justice. Political advocacy for the rights of marginalized communities—whether based on race, gender, disability, or sexual orientation—can lead to policy reforms that promote equality and justice. Legislation such as the Civil Rights Act, Marriage Equality laws, or Disability Rights laws are prime examples of how political influence has been used to achieve social equity.

9. Corporate and Economic Influence: Corporations and wealthy individuals can exert significant political influence, particularly through lobbying, campaign financing, and policy advocacy. The scope of corporate influence impacts trade regulations, tax policies, environmental protections, and workers' rights. Understanding this scope is essential for analysing the balance of power between the state and economic elites, particularly in capitalist democracies where business interests often hold substantial sway.

10. Cultural and Ideological Influence: Political influence also extends to cultural and ideological realms. Political leaders, media outlets, and social platforms shape public values, ideologies, and societal norms. Issues such as nationalism, patriotism, freedom of speech, and collective identity are often influenced by political discourse, impacting the way individuals view their role in society and their relationship to the state.

Conclusion:

Political influence is a fundamental force that shapes governance, policy, and societal outcomes across the globe. From the actions of political leaders and interest groups to the power of media and social movements, political influence plays a central role in determining how societies address critical issues and navigate complex challenges. Its scope spans a wide range of areas, including policy formation, electoral processes, government accountability, social movements, and international relations. While political influence has the potential to drive positive change—such as advancing social justice, improving transparency, and fostering democratic engagement—it also presents risks, particularly when it leads to corruption, inequality, or the disproportionate control of power by elites. Understanding the dynamics of political influence is crucial for promoting a fairer, more transparent political system, where the interests of all groups, including marginalized populations, are represented.

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ROLE OF HEALTH IN HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX: A SPECIAL REFERENCE TO CHIKKABALLAPURA DISTRICT, KARNATAKA

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Abstract

The Human Development Index (HDI) is a widely accepted metric for assessing a region's well-being, encompassing three essential dimensions: life expectancy at birth, expected years of schooling, and Gross National Income per capita. Among these dimensions, health plays a pivotal role in determining the overall HDI of a region. This paper analyses into the significance of health in HDI, with a specific focus on Chikkaballapura district in Karnataka, India.

Introduction

The Human Development Index (HDI) is a crucial metric that assesses a region's well-being by considering three essential dimensions: life expectancy at birth (health), expected years of schooling (education), and Gross National Income per capita (income). In the context of Chikkaballapura district, Karnataka, health plays a vital role in determining the district's HDI.

Chikkaballapura district, located in the state of Karnataka, India, faces numerous health-related challenges. The district has a population of approximately 1.5 million people, with a significant proportion living in rural areas. The district's health indicators, such as life expectancy, infant mortality rate, and maternal mortality rate, are below the national averages.

Objectives

The primary objective of this study is to examine the role of health in HDI, with a specific focus on Chikkaballapura district, Karnataka. The study aims to:

1. Analyze the current health status of Chikkaballapura district.
2. Examine the relationship between health and HDI.
3. Identify strategies to improve health outcomes and HDI in Chikkaballapura district.

Methodology

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis methods. The study uses secondary data sources, such as the National Family Health Survey (NFHS) and the Casual visit to hospital and Interact with Patience's General to analyze the health status of Chikkaballapura district. Primary data collection involves conducting in-depth interviews with healthcare professionals, policymakers, and community leaders.

Role of Health in HDI

Health is a critical component of the HDI, as it directly affects an individual's quality of life and productivity. In Karnataka, the health indices vary significantly across districts. For instance, Raichur district has the highest health index, while Bangalore has the lowest infant mortality rate ¹.

Challenges in Chikkaballapura District

Chikkaballapura district faces several health-related challenges, including:

- **1. Limited access to healthcare services:** The district has a shortage of healthcare facilities and professionals, making it difficult for residents to access quality healthcare.

- **2. High infant mortality rates:** The district has a high infant mortality rate, which is a critical indicator of the overall health and well-being of a region.

- **3. Low life expectancy:** The district has a lower life expectancy compared to other districts in Karnataka, which is a concern for the overall health and well-being of the residents.

Strategies for Improvement

To improve the health outcomes in Chikkaballapura district, the following strategies can be implemented:

- **1. Increasing access to healthcare services:** Establishing more healthcare facilities and recruiting additional healthcare professionals can help improve access to quality healthcare.

- **2. Improving the quality of healthcare services:** Providing training to healthcare professionals, upgrading healthcare infrastructure, and implementing quality control measures can help improve the quality of healthcare services.

- **3. Promoting health education and awareness:** Conducting health education programs, promoting healthy behaviors, and providing information on disease prevention and management can help promote health awareness among residents.

Conclusion

In conclusion, health plays a vital role in determining the HDI of Chikkaballapura district, Karnataka. Addressing the health-related challenges in the district requires a multi-faceted approach that includes increasing access to healthcare services, improving the quality of healthcare services, and promoting health education and awareness. By implementing these strategies, the district can improve its health outcomes and overall HDI.

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AN OVER VIEW OF CONSTITUENT ASSEMBLY DEBATES OF GANDHI, AMBEDKAR ON THE ESTABLISHMENTS OF VILLAGE PANCHAYATS IN INDIA

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Abstract

Mahatma Gandhi envisioned that a free India would rest on a foundation of gram panchayats, village republics that governed locally and epitomized Swaraj in practice. B.R. Ambedkar was sceptical; he described the caste-ridden, unequal village society as a cesspool. Yet, he was not unequivocally against decentralisation. Yet, the progress of panchayati raj has been patchy, since from the establishment of Indian constitution. Some States have walked the talk by devolving untied grants to panchayats so that they can plan flexibly and implement locally relevant initiatives. However, in most, the substantive spirit of the constitutional design has been obstructed by politicians and bureaucrats, who fear the loss of their patronage powers. Panchayats are not given enough funds and are bypassed by State-controlled line departments that continue to implement programmes falling within the rightful domain of the former.

In contrast, Karnataka typifies the stop-start approach of most States to strengthening local governments. Its politicians play a double game. For political reasons they have passed laws that create a powerful framework for democratic decentralisation. But in practice the panchayats are tied down through restricted finance and administrative controls, parallel structures, and have deputed officers who owe allegiance to their line departments rather than to the elected panchayat body. Most bureaucrats support and implement this charade of devolution.

However the article will establish an argument made by the fathers of the Indian Constitution, by discussing the facts as of how the village was rejected by B.R. Ambedkar and how it was contrasted by the other members to give the status of power and authority in the hands of the people in the villages.

Introduction:

Ambedkar stated in the Assembly that “the love of the intellectual Indians for the village community is of course infinite if not pathetic. It is largely due to the fulsome praise bestowed upon it by Metcalfe who described this as little republics having nearly everything they want within themselves, and almost independent of any foreign relations. The existence of these village communities each one forming a separate little state in itself has according to Metcalfe contributed more than any other cause to the preservation of the people of India, through all the revolutions and changes which they have suffered, and is in a high degree conducive to their happiness and to the enjoyment of great portion of the freedom and independence. No doubt the village communities have lasted where nothing else lasts”.

He concluded his comment by stating, “What is a village but a sink of localism, a den of ignorance, narrow-mindedness and communalism? I am glad that the Draft Constitution has discarded the village and adopted the individual as its unit”. November 4, 1949 is a moment in the history of India when liberal democracy was founded on the individual as the unit. And the individual overrode the village – the most chastised unit of Indian social life. In this way, Ambedkar’s that part of speech which critiqued Indian village has twofold significance in the construction of post-colonial modernity. Ambedkar broke the imaginary construction of the village as the ideal social space. Simplicity, tradition, closeness with nature, a great sense of community, etc. were attached with the meaning of the village. He provided an opposite picture of the village as a social space of human degradation. Secondly, it was a statement which confronted and contested Gandhi’s idea of Hind Swaraj. However he was not alone in his views on the Indian village life.

Gandhi's Views

Gandhi believed that in order to attain true freedom we would have to live in villages. He wrote to Nehru, "You will not understand me if you think that I am talking about the villages of today "My villages today exist in my imagination...." "After all, every person lives in the world of his own imagination". He then outlined the village of his imagination, "The villager in this imagined village will not be apathetic – he will embody pure consciousness. He will not lead his life like an animal in a squalid dark room. Men and women will live freely and be prepared to face the whole world. The village will not know cholera, plague or smallpox. No one will live indolently, nor luxuriously"

It is clear from the above that Gandhi was building a utopia, but in the process, at the same time, he was constructing the Indian nation and showing the way for nation-building. His answer implicated an altogether different notion of India, Nehru's notion representing European modernity. He wrote, "Briefly put, my view is that the question before us is not one of truth versus untruth or non-violence versus violence I do not understand why a village should necessarily embody truth and non-violence. A village, normally speaking, is backward intellectually and culturally and no progress can be made from a backward environment. Narrow-minded people are much likely to be untruthful and violent.

Village as an Important Unit

In the light of the above knowledge about Nehru's views on village, one could easily assume that Nehru was on the side of Ambedkar with regard to his views on Indian villages which he made part of his speech. Reminding oneself that Gandhi and his ideology had permeated into the Congress cadres it is also possible to look back at the reaction of some of the members of the Constituent Assembly. It began immediately after Ambedkar moved the Draft Constitution for discussion, which began on November 5, 1948. After the preliminary discussion on modalities, expressions and legalities, the first to make comment on Ambedkar's views on village was HV Kamath who said, One thing I join issue with Dr. Ambedkar. He was pleased to refer to the villages..... as "sinks of localism and dens of ignorance, narrow- mindedness and communalism"; and the "pathetic faith" in village communities. He contended that Ambedkar's attitude towards the village was that of an 'urban highbrow' and was not acceptable. He then went on to identify the problem in terms of the urban background of the members of the Drafting Committee and pointed out that with the exception of Sriyut Munshi none of them had participated in the freedom struggle. He then went on to underline that India's ancient polity was organised around village communities which were autonomous and self-contained'. Obvious implication of such an emphasis was that the villages were indispensable for the political life of the country. He further added, "I believe the day is not distant when not merely India but the whole world, if it wants peace and security and happiness, will have to decentralise and establish village republics and town republics, and on the basis of this they will have to build their State; otherwise the world is in for hard times". Said Kamath.

Attempt To Set Autonomous Village Panchayats

On the same day in the afternoon, that is, November 6, 1948, K. Santhanam from Madras, who served as railway minister in Nehru's cabinet, while referring to Ambedkar's comments on village, said, "I do not agree with his condemnation of the village panchayats and his statement that they are responsible for all the national disasters". As a matter of fact, he opined, despite all changes the villages have preserved the Indian culture and saved society from anarchy. An attempt should be made to set autonomous village panchayats for which there is a need for such provision in the Constitution, because "in the long run local autonomy for each village must constitute the basic framework for the future

freedom of this country". The same day, Pandit Thakur Dass Bhargava from East Punjab, after a long speech touching on various aspects of the Draft Constitution, spoke on what and how the village India should exist by assuming that Ambedkar's views on it had been negated.

He misunderstood Ambedkar in the sense that when he introduced the Draft Constitution, his speech touched upon the village in terms of what would be the unit of Indian citizenship – individual or collective. In the process of elimination and with the knowledge that Gandhi had extolled villages, he argued that village could not be the unit of citizenship. However, the matter was clearly discerned by some of the members among whom many chose to ignore the issue of village, but some of them took it up quite seriously.

The discussion on the Draft Constitution, as had been decided by the Vice-President, Dr. H. C. Mookherjee, who was chairing the proceedings of the Assembly in the absence of the President, was to be concluded on November 8, 1948. When the Vice-President asked Alladi Krishanaswami Ayyar from Madras, there were still forty members who had not got the time to speak. Ayyar started his speech by saying that "I do not share the views of my honourable Friend in his condemnation of village communities in India". He then went on to summarise the debate so far had taken place. He touched upon the issue of village in the following manner:

The constitution does not give sufficient importance to village communities, which are an essential feature of India's social and political life. With the large powers vested in the provincial or state legislatures in regard to local self- government and other matters, there is nothing to prevent the provincial legislatures, from constituting the villages as administrative units for discharge of various functions vested in the state government. It should be reminded that Ayyar was member of the Drafting Committee, which means that he largely agreed with Ambedkar on the question of individual as unit, but he might have felt that villages could be the administrative units in certain ways.

On November 9, 1948, the first person to take into consideration the issue of village was Prof. N. G. Ranga from Madras. He said, "I am most unhappy that Dr. Ambedkar should have said what he has said about village panchayats". He asserted that Ambedkar had no knowledge of the village panchayats in Southern India. Rather than reading the history of other countries, he should have read Indian history, he said. He also argued that instead of centralisation India needed decentralised administration in which the village as a unit would play the most important role. For Prof. Ranga village symbolised decentralisation. It will be important to quote some of his lines to have taste of his language of ideas thus. The necessity for providing as many political institutions as possible in order to enable our villagers to gain as much experience in democratic institutions as possible in order to be able to discharge their responsibilities through adult suffrage in the new democracy that we are going to establish. Without this foundation stone of village panchayats in our country, how would it be possible for our masses to play their rightful part in our democracy?

On November 9, 1948, Moturi Satyanarayana from Madras brought up the issue of Swaraj with regard to village without criticising Ambedkar. He said, "The people know what swaraj means. But only the international view-point, and not the national nor the swaraj, nor even the villagers' view-point, is being given weight in the framing of this Constitution". It is interesting to note that most of the speakers including Satyanarayana placed in the centre of their discourse the thirty years of struggle. It seems that the period they had been identifying as a phase in national struggle was the one during which Gandhi became the main political and ideological force.

Constitutional Status for the Village Panchayats

On November 22, 1948, after the Article 31 was added to the Constitution after discussion and amendments, a new Article 31-A as an amendment was moved in the Assembly. It was amendment No. 927 which stood by the name of M. Ananthasayanam Ayyangar who prayed to the Vice-President that K. Santhanam's amendment was better worded than his and should be taken for discussion. The Vice-President accepted his request and asked K. Santhanam to move the amendment who did so thus after article 31, the following new article be added:-'31-A. The State shall take steps to organise village panchayats and endow them with such powers and authority as may be necessary to enable them to function as units of self-government'. Santhanam went on to elaborate that many other members had proposed similar amendments.

He emphasised that how much power was to be given to the village panchayats was a matter which would vary from state to state. He added, "What is attempted to do here is to give a definite and unequivocal direction that the state shall take steps to organise panchayats and shall endow them with necessary powers and authority to enable them to function as units of self-government". Immediately after Santhanam completed his speech, Ambedkar was on his feet and said, "Sir, I accept the amendment'. It seems that the pressure of the Gandhians, who considered Ambedkar as the opponent, might have weighed on him to accept the amendment. It should be reminded that with the Congress majority in the Assembly, the amendment could have been adopted and added to the Constitution even if Ambedkar had opposed it.

It might have been assumed that once Ambedkar accepted the amendment, the matter was finally settled, but it did not happen in that manner. Some members still felt the need to remind Ambedkar how erroneous his views about Indian villages were. T. Prakasam, the future chief minister of Andhra Pradesh and destined to be remembered as Andhra Kesri, was the first to create ripples in the minds of the modernists who might be sharing with Ambedkar the view about Indian villages. He said, Sir, a very serious situation was created by not making the village republic or the village unit as the real basis of the Constitution. It must be acknowledged on all hands that this is a construction which is begun at the top and which is going down to the bottom.

Conclusion:

Ours is an ancient, a very ancient country and the village has had always an important position here. In Greece, for instance, towns had greater importance than villages. The Republics of Athens and Sparta occupy a very important place in the world history today. But no importance was attached by them to the villages. But in our country the village occupied such an important position that even in the legends contained in most ancient books – Upanishads – if there are descriptions of the forest retreats, of the sages, there are also descriptions of villages. Modern historians have also admitted this fact. The Vice-President commented that all these speeches were nothing except praising the amendment and then he moved the amendment which was passed and the Article 31-A was added to the Constitution on November 22, 1948.

Upendranath Barman from West Bengal argued for the immediate formation of village panchayats and the transfer of power to them and opined that 'many of the problems of governing this country will be solved'. Next day on November 23, 1949, B. P. Jhunjhunwala from Bihar focused more on the issue of village than any other matter in his speech. He began his comment on the village by criticising the centralisation of power. He said, Sir, I do not believe in the theory propounded here that everything should be centralised and that the whole country should be governed from the Centre. But I agree that powers should be given to the Centre so that in times of emergency they can be utilised for

the benefit of the people. Sir, the Centre should have only such power as is necessary and cannot be exercised by its component governing parts, for the preservation of the unity and integration of the whole of India. Every other power should be, as much as possible, decentralised and given to the unit of village or groups of villages what to say Province. With that purpose in view, I had given notice of an amendment to the Preamble that 'after the word "Republic" the words "to be worked on the basis of autonomous village Units or groups of villages organised on the principle of self-sufficiency as far as practical" be added.

The above view was stated to be in accordance with Gandhian values – an idea of self-sufficient village as unit of governance and self-rule. After suggesting the needed amendment of the Preamble of the Indian Constitution, Jhunjhunwala went on to quote most of the speech on the village delivered by Dr. B. R. Ambedkar when he moved the Draft Constitution for debate on November 4, 1948. After reading Ambedkar's views on village, he said, "Nothing can be more uncharitable and unjust to the villagers than what Dr. Ambedkar has said". Same day Dip Narayan Sinha from Bihar emphasised the importance of Indian villages as the custodians of the civilisation, whereas most of the countries of the world are turning to the cities.

O. V. Alagesan from Madras was the last speaker to mention the issue of village at length and after him village did not figure in the speeches of the members. He also tended to respond to those members' views who thought that village had not been adequately covered in the Constitution. He said, "What was conceived under the village unit system was that the village voters would be called upon to elect the Panchayats and only the members of the Panchayats were to take part in the elections to the various assemblies, Provincial and Central. But now, it is the village voter himself who will be called upon to weigh the issues before the country and elect his representative, and so he will directly participate in the election".

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ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಲಂಬಾಣಿಗರಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾನದ ಅರಿವು

ಡಾ|| ಜಿ.ಎಲ್.ರಜಪೂತ

ಸಹಾಯಕ ಪ್ರಾಧ್ಯಾಪಕರು ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ವಿಭಾಗ
ಎಸ್.ಎಸ್. ಹಾಗೂ ಟಿ.ಪಿ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಮಹಾವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ,
ಸಂಕೇಶ್ವರ

ಮಾನವ ಸ್ವಭಾವತಃ ಸಮಾಜ ಜೀವಿಯಾಗಿರುವಂತೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಜೀವಿಯೂ ಆಗಿದ್ದಾನೆ" ಎಂಬ ಮಾತನ್ನು ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಜ್ಞ, ಅರಿಸ್ಟಾಟಲ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇದರಿಂದ ತಿಳಿದು ಬರುವುದೇನೆಂದರೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕಾಲದಿಂದಲೂ ಎಲ್ಲರ ಗಮನವನ್ನು ತನ್ನಡೆಗೆ ಸೆಳೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಇತಿಹಾಸದೊಡಕೂ ಜನ ಇದರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಆಸಕ್ತಿ ತಳೆದಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬಹುದು ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಯಾವುದೇ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನವಿರಲಿ ಅಥವಾ ಚಿಂತನೆ ಇರಲಿ ಅಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ, ಆಡಳಿತ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಆಳುವವರು ಆಳಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವವರು. ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಜನಾಭಿಪ್ರಾಯ ಆಸಕ್ತಿ ಗುಂಪು ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ ವಿಷಯಗಳಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಈ ಎಲ್ಲ ಒಟ್ಟು ವಿಷಯಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡ ವಿಷಯ ಅಥವಾ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರವನ್ನು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಅಥವಾ ರಾಜಕಾರಣವೆಂದು ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ.

ಯಾವುದೇ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಿಂದ ದೂರ ಉಳಿಯದಾದಲೇ ಅಥವಾ ಪ್ರಭಾವಿತನಾಗದೇ ಇರುಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಿಲ್ಲ. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಇಷ್ಟಪಡಲಿ ಅಥವಾ ಬಿಡಲಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಯಾವುದಾದರೊಂದು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಗೆ ಒಳಪಟ್ಟಿರುತ್ತಾನೆ. ಅಲ್ಲದೆ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯೂ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ನಗರ, ಶಾಲೆ ಕಾಲೇಜು, ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಸಂಘಗಳ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾಲ್ಗೊಂಡಿರುತ್ತಾನೆ. ಆದುದರಿಂದ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ಮಾನವನ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಾಸುಹೊಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಬೆರೆತುಕೊಂಡಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ನಾಗರಿಕನು ಪ್ರತ್ಯಕ್ಷವಾದರೂ ಅಥವಾ ಪರೋಕ್ಷವಾದರೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಾನೆ. ಹಿಂದೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವಿಷಯಗಳು ಬಗ್ಗೆ ರಾಜ ಮಹಾರಾಜರು ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ಹಾಗೂ ದಾರ್ಶನಿಕರ ಮಾತ್ರ ಆಸಕ್ತಿ ವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ಪರಿಣಾಮವಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಆ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವವರ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ ಸೀಮಿತವಾಗಿದ್ದಿತು.

ಜನ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯರಿಗೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕಾರ್ಯಕಲಾಪಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಅಷ್ಟಾಗಿ ಅವಕಾಶವಿರಲಿಲ್ಲ. ಇದರಿಂದ ಆತನು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರ ವಿಷಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಆಸಕ್ತಿ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿರಲಿಲ್ಲ. ಇನ್ನೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವಿಷಯಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಆಸಕ್ತಿ ವಹಿಸುವುದು ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ಜನಾಂಗದವರ ದೊರದ ಮಾತಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಆದರೆ ಯಾವಾಗ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಪದ್ಧತಿ ಉದಯವಾಯಿತೋ ಆಗ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಮೇಲಿನ ಕೆಲವೇ ಕೆಲವು ಜನರ ಸ್ವಾಮ್ಯ ಕೊನೆಗೊಂಡಿತು ಆಧುನಿಕ ಯುಗದ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯು ಒಂದಿಲ್ಲ ಒಂದು ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇನ್ನೂ ನಾವು ಹಲವಾರು ಅರ್ಥದಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿದು ಕೊಳ್ಳಲುಬಹುದು 'ರಾಜ್ಯದ ನೀತಿರೂಪಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಆ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದ ನಾಗರಿಕರು ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯಾಗಿದೆ' ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಎಂದರೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಹಂಚುವ ವರ್ತನೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರಭಾವಿಸುವುದಾಗಿದೆ ತಮ್ಮ ನಾಯಕರನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡಲು ಸಮಾಜ ಒಂದರ ಸದಸ್ಯರು ಇಚ್ಛಾ ಪೂರ್ವಕ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳು & ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ನೀತಿಯನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತ್ಯಕ್ಷವಾಗಿ ಇಲ್ಲದೇ ಪರೋಕ್ಷವಾಗಿ ಪಾತ್ರ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುವುದನ್ನು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಬಹುದು.

ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯ ಸ್ವಭಾವ

ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯ ಅರ್ಹತೆಯನ್ನು ಅವಲಂಬಿಸಿದೆ. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯು ಸಮಾಜದೊಳಗೆ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಗೆ ಬರುವ ಅವಕಾಶವಾದರೂ ಅದು ಒಂದು ಕಲೆಯಂತೆ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಕೊಂಡಾಗ ಆತನ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ ವಿಸ್ತಾರಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ರಾಜಕೀಯಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ವಿಶೇಷ ಜ್ಞಾನ ತರಬೇತಿ ಬೇಕೆಂದೇನು ಇಲ್ಲ. ಆದರೂ ಕೂಡಾ ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ಜನರಲ್ಲಿ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕರಣದಿಂದ ಪ್ರಾಪ್ತವಾಗುವಂತಹದು.

ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳ ಅವಲಂಬನೆ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಕುರಿತು ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯ ವ್ಯಕ್ತ ಪಡಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಮತಚಲಾವಣೆ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾಲ್ಗೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಾಮೀತ ಅವಕಾಶಗಳು ಎಲ್ಲ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಲಭ್ಯವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಆದರೆ ಪ್ರತಿವಿಧಿಗಳಾಗಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರದ ಸ್ಥಾನಮಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಲು ವಿಶೇಷವಾದ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಕೂಡಾ ಲಂಬಾಣಿಗರ ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಆರ್ಥಿಕವಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಅವಲಂಬಿಸಿದೆ.

ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಇದೊಂದು ಹಕ್ಕಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ, ಪ್ರವಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮಾನತೆ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಭಾತ್ಯತ್ವ ಹಾಗೂ ಸಹ ಭಾಗಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಬದ್ಧವಾಗಿಯೇ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಿರುವುದು ಕಂಡು ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಇಲ್ಲ ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ಜನರು ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕವಾಗಿ ಹಿಂದೂಳಿದಿದ್ದಾರೆ

ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುವ ಅಂಶಗಳು

ಒಂದು ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಹತ್ತು ಹಲವು ಅಂಶಗಳ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುತ್ತವೆ. ಈ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುವ ಅಂಶಗಳು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಹೀಗೆ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬಹುದು. ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಗಮನಿಸಿದಾಗ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಜಾಣತನ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯಹೊಂದಿದ್ದ ಸಂಪತ್ತು ಅವನು ಗಳಿಸಿಕೊಂಡ ಗೌರವ ಅವನಲ್ಲರುವ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆ ಅಥವಾ ಅರಿವು ಹಾಗೂ ಅವನಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಕಾರಣ ಇವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯ ಹಲವು ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆ ಮೇಲೆ ಖಚಿತವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುವ ಈ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಅಂಶಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ನಮ್ಮ ದೇಶದ ಜನತೆಗೆ ಗಮನಿಸಿದಾಗ ಹಲವು ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು. ದುರ್ಬಲ ದಲಿತ ವರ್ಗ, ಹಿಂದೂಳುವಿಕೆ, ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರು, ಲಂಬಾಣಿಗರು, ಈ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ವರ್ಗದ ಮೇಲೆ ಹೇಳಿದ ಅಂಶಗಳಿಂದ ದೂರ ಇರುವುದು ನಾವು ಕಾಣುತ್ತದೆ.

ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಲಂಬಾಣಿಗರ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ

ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತವಾದ ಜನಪ್ರಿಯ ಸಾರ್ವಭೌಮಾಧಿಕಾರ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತದ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ರಚಿಸುವ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನವನ್ನು ಮಾಡುವ ಇಚ್ಛೆ ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದೇವೆ ಜನಪ್ರಿಯ ಸಾರ್ವಭೌಮಾಧಿಕಾರ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತದ ಕೆಲವು ಮೂಲಭೂತಾಂಶಗಳಾದ ಪ್ರದರ್ಶನ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ವೇದಿಕೆಗಳ ಮುಖಾಂತರ ತಮ್ಮ ಅಶೋತ್ತರಗಳನ್ನು ಪೂರೈಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಚಲಾಯಿಸುವುದು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಚಾರ ಮಾಡಿಸುವುದು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವುದು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಪಡೆಯುವುದು ಇವುಗಳನ್ನು ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿಟ್ಟುಕೊಂಡು ಈ ಹಂತಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ಜನರು ಚುನಾವನೆಯ ಮತದಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾವ ರೀತಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಸೈದ್ಧಾಂತಿಕವಾಗಿ ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಿ ಅದರ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ನಾವು ರಚಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದ ಊಹೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲನೆಗೆ ಒಳಪಡಿಸಬಹುದು. ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿದಲ್ಲಿ 40% ರಷ್ಟು ಜನರು ತಮ್ಮ ನಾಯಕರ ಮುಖಾಂತರ

ನೇರವಾಗಿ ಪಟ್ಟಣ ಪಂಚಾಯಿತಿಗೆ ಅರ್ಜಿ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿ ತಮಗೆ ಬೇಕಾಗಿರುವ ಸವಲತ್ತುಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡಿರುವರು ಹಾಗೂ ನಾಯಕರಾಗಿದ್ದು ಪಟ್ಟಣ ಪಂಚಾಯಿತಿ ಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದು ಸಮುದಾಯವನ್ನಾಗಿ ಇವರ ಅನುಭವಗಳನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿದಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲವೊಮ್ಮೆ ಮಾನಸಿಕ ನೋವುಗಳನ್ನು ಅನುಭವಿಸಿರುವುದು ಕಂಡು ಬರುತ್ತದೆ.

ಸಮಾನತೆಗಾಗಿ ಇವರ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳು ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರಾಗಿರುವ ಇವರು ಸಾಧಿಸಲು ಮಾಡಿದ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳ ಸೋಲುಕುಲ ಹಾಗೂ ಜನಾಂಗೀಯ ವೈರತ್ವದಿಂದ ಈ ಜನಾಂಗದ ಮೇಲೆ ಕೆಲವೊಮ್ಮೆ ಆಗಿರುವ ಅಪಘಾತಗಳು ಇವುಗಳಕ್ಕಿಂತಲೂ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಜನಾಂಗಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿದ ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜನಾಂಗ ಮತ್ತು ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ಜನರ ನಡುವಿನ ಆಂತರಿಕ ಕಲಹಗಳು ಈ ಪಟ್ಟಣ ಪಂಚಾಯತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಇವರುಂಡ ಕಹಿ ಅನುಭವಗಳಾಗಿವೆ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಕಾರ್ಯವಿಧಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಚರಣೆ ವಾಕ್ ಚಾತುರ್ಯ, ವಿಷಯ ಮಂಡನೆ, ಸಮಾಜದೊಡನೆ ಸ್ಪಂದನೆ ನಾಯಕತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಬೇಕಾಗಿರುವ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕತೆ ರಾಜ್ಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಿಂದ ದೊರಕಬೇಕಾದ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳ ಬಳಕೆ, ರಾಜ್ಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ವಿವಿಧ ಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಬೇಕಾದ ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಲಕ್ಷಣಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಅಂತಯೇ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಪಿಡಗುಗಳಾದ ಜಾತೀಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರಿಗಳಾಗುವದರಲ್ಲಿ ವಿರೋಧಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಇವರು ತಮಗೆ ಆದ ಆಗಾಧವಾದ ಅನುಭವಗಳನ್ನು ಅನ್ನು ವೆಂಬಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ಜನಾಂಗವು ತಮ್ಮ ಕೈಲಾದಷ್ಟು ಎಲ್ಲ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾಗ್ಯೂ ಮುಂದುವರೆದ ಸಮಾಜ ಮೇಲ್ವಿಚಾರಣೆ ಗುಂಪು ಹಾಗೂ ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿಯವರೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ ವಿಲೀನವಾಗಿ ಕಾರ್ಯವನ್ನು ಸಾಗಲೂ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಇವರಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಹಣವುಳ್ಳವರು ಹಾಗೂ ನಗರದ ಜನವರ್ಗವು ಪ್ರಗತಿಪರ ಆಲೋಚನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹಂಚಿಕೊಳ್ಳದೇ ಪರಸ್ಪರ ಸಹಾಯಕಾರಿಯಾಗದೇ ಇರುವ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಜನಾಂಗದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಮೇಲುಕೀಳು ಎಂಬ ಭಾವನೆಗಳು ಮೂಡಿವೆ ಬಡವರು ತಮ್ಮ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಬದ್ಧರಾಗಿದ್ದು ಕೆಲವೊಮ್ಮೆ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಿಂದ ತಮಗೆ ದೊರಕಬೇಕಾದ ಸವಲತ್ತುಗಳಿಂದ ವಂಚಿತರಾಗಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬಹುದು ಪಟ್ಟಣ ಪಂಚಾಯಿತಿಯಂಥ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ವರ್ಗಕ್ಕೆ ಅನುಕೂಲ ಮಾಡಿ ಕೊಡುತ್ತದೆ. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಒತ್ತಡ ಗುಂಪಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಿರುವ ಒಂದು ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯಾಗಿ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ವರ್ಗದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ವಿಭಾಗವಾಗಿ, ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನೇರ ಹಾಗೂ ಪರೋಕ್ಷ ಸದಸ್ಯರಾಗಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವರ್ತುಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾರರಾಗಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತ ಲಂಬಾಣಿಗರ ಜನರು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಜನ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸುತ್ತ ತಮ್ಮ ಉತ್ತಮ ಭವಿಷ್ಯದ ರೂಪಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಲಂಬಾಣಿಗರ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳು

ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ಜನರು ಇಂದಿಗೂ ಅಲಕ್ಷಿತ ವರ್ಗವಾಗಿಯೇ ಉಳಿದಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಅವರಿಗೆ ನಿರಾಕರಿಸಲಾಗಿತ್ತದೆ. ಅದರ ಭಾರತ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯವಾದ. ನಂತರದಲ್ಲಿ ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಮತದಾನದ ಹಕ್ಕು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಅವಕಾಶ ಮತ್ತು ಕಾನೂನು ಬದ್ಧ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಯಿತು. ಆದರೂ ಕೂಡ ಇವತ್ತಿಗೂ ಅವರು ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ ಸಂಘಟಿತ ಶಕ್ತಿಯಾಗಿ ಬೆಳೆದು ಬಂದಿಲ್ಲ ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವೇನೆಂದರೆ:-

- 1) ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಅರಿವಿನ ಕೊರತೆ.
- 2] ಅನಕ್ಷರತೆ/ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿ.
- 3] ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿ

4] ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆ

5] ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿ.

6] ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ತಾಂಡಾಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಕ್ಕಳ ಮಾರಾಟ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಪಿಡುಗಾಗಿ ಕಾಡುತ್ತಿರುವ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆ.

ಶತ ಶತಮಾನಗಳಿಂದ ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದ ಭಾಷೆ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ ವೇಷ ಭೂಷಣವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿ ಎಲ್ಲರ ಗಮನ ಸೆಳೆಯುವ ಈ ಜನತೆಯ ಇತಿಹಾಸ ಅಷ್ಟೇ ಕಷ್ಟದ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಬಂದಿದೆ ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ಜನಾಂಗದವರು ತ್ಯಾಗಿಗಳ ಸರಳ ಮನಸ್ಸಿನ ಸಹೃದಯಗಳೆಂದು ತಿಳಿದ ಉನ್ನತವರ್ಗದವರು ತಮ್ಮ ದಾಸ್ಯಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದು ವಿಷಾಧನೀಯಸಂಗತಿ ಈ ರೀತಿ ತ್ಯಾಗ ಮನೋಭಾವನೆ ಹೊಂದಿದ ಈ ಜನ ತಮಗಾಗಿ ಇರಲು ಸರಿಯಾದ ನೆಲೆ ಇಲ್ಲದೆ ಅಲೆಮಾರಿಗಳಾಗಿ ಸರ್ಕಾರದವರು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸಿದೆ. ಹೆದ್ದಾರಿ ರೈಲ್ವೆದಾರಿಗಳು, ರಸ್ತೆ ಸೇತುವೆ ಇನ್ನೂ ಅನೇಕ ಕಾಮಗಾರಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡಿ ಮೈಯ ಬೆವರು ಸುರಿಸಿ ಕಷ್ಟ ಪಟ್ಟು ದುಡಿದು ಜೀವನ ಸಾಗಿಸುತ್ತಾ ಬಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇದರಿಂದ ಕಷ್ಟ ಜೀವಿಗಳು ಸ್ವಾವಲಂಬಿಗಳೆಂದು ಹೆಸರು ಪಡೆದ ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ಜನಾಂಗವು ಯಾರಿಗೂ ಬೇಡದವಲ್ಲ. ಇಂತಹ ಸ್ವಾಭೀಮಾನದ ಲಂಬಾಣಿಗರ ಮುಗ್ಧ ಜನತೆಯು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಂಚಿತರಾಗಿ ದೂರವಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಲವಾರು ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಿದ್ದು, ಇವು ಜಿಲ್ಲೆ ತಾಲೂಕು ಹಾಗೇ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಮಟ್ಟದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಸ್ವರೂಪಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದು, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ ಸ್ವಾಯತ್ತೆಯನ್ನು ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ಕೆಲವು ಸ್ವರೂಪಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿವೆ. ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಗೆ ನಗರೀಕರಣದ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಈ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ಕಾರ್ಯಚರಣೆಗಾಗಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನಾಂಶ ಜನರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಉಪಸಂಹಾರ

ಆಧುನಿಕ ಸಮಾಜವು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ವಿಫಲ ಪ್ರಮಾಣದ ಅವಕಾಶಗಳನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸಿದ್ದರೂ ಈ ಮೇಲಿನ ಮಿತಿಗಳು ಜನರ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ನಿರಾಸೆಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದುದರಿಂದ ಜನರ ನೈಜವಾದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯ ಜನ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳ ನಡವಳಿಕೆಯ ಪರಿವರ್ತನೆಯನ್ನು ಹಾಗೂ ವಿಶಾಲ ಮನೋಭಾವನೆಯನ್ನು ಅಪೇಕ್ಷಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಅಲ್ಲದೇ ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ಜನರಿಗೆ ತಮ್ಮ ಹಕ್ಕು ಬಾಧ್ಯತೆಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅರಿವನ್ನುಂಟು ಮಾಡಲು ಅವರನ್ನು ಸುಶಿಕ್ಷಿತರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡಬೇಕು. ಇದಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಜನರು ಯೋಗ್ಯ ಪ್ರಮಾಣಿಕ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಜನರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಕಳಕಳಿ ಹೊಂದುವ ಸಚ್ಚಾರಿತ್ರಿವುಳ್ಳ ಜನಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳ ಆಯ್ಕೆಗೊಂಡು ರಾಜೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರವು ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯಿಂದ ನಳನಳಿಸಬೇಕು. ಅಂದಾಗ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ನಿಜವಾದ ಬೆಲೆ ಪ್ರಾಪ್ತವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಜೊತೆಗೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸುವತ್ತ ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ಜನತೆ ದಾವಿಸಿ ಬರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಅಂಥ ಪರಿಸರವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸುವುದು ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬರ ಅಧ್ಯ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಬಹುದು.

ಆಧಾರ ಗ್ರಂಥಗಳು:-

1] 'ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಶೋಧನಾ ವಿಧಾನಗಳು' ಉಮೇಶ ಮುಳ್ಳೂರ: ಕೆ.ಎಂ. ಮಹೇಶ್ವರ ಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಮಾಲೀಕರು ಮುದ್ರಣ ಬಳ್ಳಾರಿ.

2] ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, "ಪೂ" ಎನ್. ಹಾಲಪ್ಪ ಎಂ. ಇ. ಎಸ್. ಗುರು ಕುಲ ಪಬ್ಲಿಕೇಷನ್ಸ್ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು-2011.

3] ಇಲಿ ಆಂಡ್ ಅರ್ಬನ್ ಪಾಲಿಟಿಕ್ಸ್ ವಿಜಯ ಲಕ್ಷಂ ಪಂಡಿತ್ ಮಿತ್ರಲ್ ಪಬ್ಲಿಕೇಷನ್ ನ್ಯೂದೆಲಿ

4] ಅಖಿಲ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಬಂಜಾರ ವೇದಿಕೆ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಇವರ ಕೈಪಿಡಿ-1996-97.

5] ಬಂಜಾರ ವಾಣಿ-2024 CPÉÆÖÁšgÀ .

6] ಅಂತರ್ಜಾಲ

ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಯುವಜನರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ: ನಿರೀಕ್ಷೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಕುರಿತ ಒಂದು ಅಧ್ಯಯನ

ಡಾ. ಅರುಣಕುಮಾರ್ ಪಿ.

ಉಪನ್ಯಾಸಕರು

ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಪ್ರಥಮ ದರ್ಜೆ ಕಾಲೇಜು

ಚಿಕ್ಕನಾಯಕನಹಳ್ಳಿ

ಶ್ರೀ ಪುಟ್ಟಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಎಮ್.ಟಿ.

ಸಹಾಯಕ ಪ್ರಾಧ್ಯಾಪಕರು

ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಪ್ರಥಮ ದರ್ಜೆ ಕಾಲೇಜು

ಚಿಕ್ಕನಾಯಕನಹಳ್ಳಿ

ಸಾರಾಂಶ

ಒಬ್ಬ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ತನ್ನ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಮಾನತೆ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನ್ಯಾಯವನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಇರುವ ಏಕೈಕ ಅವಕಾಶವೆಂದರೆ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಬ್ರಿಟಿಷರಿಂದ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಪಡೆದ ಭಾರತವು ತನ್ನದೇ ಆದ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಆಡಳಿತ ಮಾಡಲು ಪ್ರಥಮ ಭಾರಿ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು 1952ರಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾರಂಭಿಸಿತು. ಅಂದಿನಿಂದ ಇಂದಿನವರೆಗೆ (2024) 17 ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪೂರ್ಣಗೊಳಿಸಿದೆ. ಈ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜನರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯು ತುಂಬಾ ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನವು 1988ರವರೆಗೆ ಮತದಾನದ ವಯಸ್ಸನ್ನು 21 ವರ್ಷಕ್ಕೆ ಸೀಮಿತಗೊಳಿಸಿತ್ತು. ತದನಂತರ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಕ್ಕೆ 61ನೇ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಯನ್ನು ತಂದು ಮತದಾನದ ವಯಸ್ಸನ್ನು 18 ವರ್ಷ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಗೆ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಈ ಮೂಲಕ ಮತದಾನ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಯುವಜನಾಂಗಕ್ಕೆ ಮತ್ತಷ್ಟು ಅವಕಾಶ ಲಭಿಸಿದಂತಾಯಿತು. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆಗಳ ಸದಸ್ಯ ಸ್ಥಾನಕ್ಕೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲು ಕನಿಷ್ಠ 25 ವರ್ಷವನ್ನು ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜ್ಯಸಭೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿಧಾನಪರಿಷತ್ ಸದಸ್ಯ ಸ್ಥಾನಗಳಿಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲು ಕನಿಷ್ಠ 30 ವರ್ಷ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಿತು. ಇದರ ಪರಿಣಾಮವಾಗಿ ಯುವ ಜನಾಂಗಕ್ಕೆ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಅತಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಅವಕಾಶ ದೊರಕಿತಾಯಿತು. ಈ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಯುವಜನರು ಹೇಗೆ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಯಾವ ರೀತಿಯ ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ತಿಳಿದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಈ ಲೇಖನದ ಉದ್ದೇಶವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪದಗಳು: ಚುನಾವಣೆ, ಮತದಾನ, ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಸುವುದು, ಸಂವಿಧಾನ, ಯುವಜನಾಂಗ, ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ.

ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಯುವಜನರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ: ನಿರೀಕ್ಷೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಕುರಿತ ಒಂದು ಅಧ್ಯಯನ

1. ಪೀಠಿಕೆ:

ಭಾರತ ಒಂದು ಬೃಹತ್ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾಗಿದ್ದು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಹೊಂದುತ್ತಿರುವ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳ ನಾಯಕನಾಗಿ ವಿಶ್ವದ ಗಮನ ಸೆಳೆಯುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಸತ್ಯ ಸಂಗತಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣ ನಮ್ಮ ದೇಶದ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಜನತೆಯ ಸಕ್ರಿಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯು ಬಹುಮುಖ್ಯ ಅಂಶವಾಗಿದೆ. ನಮ್ಮ ದೇಶದ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಆಳುವ ಮತ್ತು ಆಳಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಅವಕಾಶ ಇಲ್ಲಿನ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಬದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ಲಭ್ಯವಾಗಿರುವ ಅವಕಾಶವಾಗಿದೆ. ಅಂದರೆ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಹಾಗೂ ಮತ ಚಲಾಯಿಸುವ ಹಕ್ಕನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾವನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿಸಿರುವಂತೆ ಈ ದೇಶದ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳಿಗೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಮಾನತೆ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನ್ಯಾಯವನ್ನು ದೊರಕಿಸಿಕೊಡುವ ಉದ್ದೇಶವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಈ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಇಲ್ಲಿನ ಜನರು ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತ್ಯಕ್ಷವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪರೋಕ್ಷವಾಗಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರವಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಸಂಸತ್ತಿನ ಕೆಳಮನೆಯಾದ ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗದ ಕೆಳಮನೆಯಾದ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಾಗಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಮತ್ತು ಮತದಾನ ಮಾಡಲು ಅವಕಾಶವನ್ನು ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಮೂಲಕ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದ ಜನರು ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಮುಂದುವರೆದು ನೋಡುವುದಾದರೆ, ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಬಂದ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಇದ್ದ ಮತದಾರರ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಗೂ ಹಾಗೂ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಇರುವ ಮತದಾರರ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಗೂ ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸವಿದೆ. ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಯುವ ಮತದಾರರ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿರುವುದು ಗಮನಿಸಬೇಕಾದ ಅಂಶವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇಂತಹ ಯುವ ಮತದಾರರು ಹಾಗೂ ಯುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿ ಹೇಗೆ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಯಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ.

2. ರಾಜಕಾರಣದ ಅರ್ಥ:

ಸರಳವಾಗಿ ಹೇಳುವುದಾದರೆ ರಾಜಕಾರಣ ಎಂದರೆ 'ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಕಾರ್ಯಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತ್ಯಕ್ಷವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪರೋಕ್ಷವಾಗಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿ ಆಡಳಿತ ನಡೆಸುವ ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಾಗಿದೆ'. ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿದ್ದ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಕ್ಕೂ ಆಧುನಿಕ ಕಾಲದ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಕ್ಕೂ ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸಗಳಿವೆ. ಗ್ರೀಕರ ಆಡಳಿತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿದಾಗ ಅಲ್ಲಿ ನಗರ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಆಡಳಿತಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ರಾಜಕಾರಣ ಸೀಮಿತವಾಗಿತ್ತು. ರೋಮನ್ನರ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕಾರಣವು ಗಣರಾಜ್ಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಗೆ ಸೀಮಿತವಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಆದರೆ ಆಧುನಿಕ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕಾರಣ ಎಂಬುದು ವಿಶಾಲ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಆಳುವವರು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡು ತಮ್ಮ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ಈಡೇರಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಅದೇ ರೀತಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗದ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳು ಆಳಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ವರ್ಗವಾಗಿದ್ದು ತಮ್ಮನ್ನು ಆಳುವ ವರ್ಗದವರನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಮೂಲಕ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.

3. ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಜನರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ:

ರಾಜಕಾರಣವೆಂಬುದು ಒಂದು ವಿಶಾಲ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರವಾಗಿದ್ದು ಜನರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯು ಅತ್ಯವಶ್ಯಕ ಹಾಗೂ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳೇ ಆಡಳಿತದ ಮೂಲ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳಿಲ್ಲದೆ ರಾಜಕಾರಣ ಪರಿಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಲಾರದು. ಭಾರತವು ಬ್ರಿಟಿಷರಿಂದ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಪಡೆಯುವ ಮುಂಚಿತವಾಗಿ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ರಚನೆಯ ಕಾರ್ಯವು ಪ್ರಾರಂಭವಾಯಿತು. ಈ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ದೇಶದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಜನರಿಗೂ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡಲಿಲ್ಲ. ಕೆಲವೇ ಜನರು ಮಾತ್ರ ಈ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ರಚನಾ ಸಮಿತಿಯ ಸದಸ್ಯರನ್ನು ಚುನಾಯಿಸಿದರು. ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ರಚನೆಯ ನಂತರ ಈ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆದ ಪ್ರಥಮ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಜನಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡಲು 21 ವರ್ಷ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪೂರೈಸಿದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಮತ್ತು ಪುರುಷ ಮತದಾರರಿಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡಲಾಯಿತು. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲು ಸಹ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಬದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ಅರ್ಹತೆ ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಎಲ್ಲರಿಗೂ ಅವಕಾಶವನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಯಿತು. ತದ ನಂತರದಲ್ಲಿ 1988ರಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾನದ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು 21ನೇ ವರ್ಷದಿಂದ 18 ವರ್ಷಕ್ಕೆ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡಲಾಯಿತು. ಪರಿಣಾಮವಾಗಿ ಅಂದಿನಿಂದ 18 ವರ್ಷ ವಯೋಮಿತಿ ಪೂರ್ಣಗೊಳಿಸಿದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಮತದಾರರು ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

3.1. ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಜನರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯ ವಿಧಾನಗಳು:

ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಜನರು ಎರಡು ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅವುಗಳೆಂದರೆ,

1. ಮತದಾರನಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ: ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಆಶಯದಂತೆ ಈ ದೇಶದ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ಪ್ರಜೆಯೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನ್ಯಾಯವನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಅರ್ಹನಾಗಿದ್ದಾನೆ. ಅಂದರೆ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ತಾನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಹಕ್ಕನ್ನು ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಿರುವ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪೂರ್ಣಗೊಳಿಸಿದ ನಂತರ ಆತ ಮತದಾನ ಮಾಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಆ ಹಕ್ಕನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ರೀತಿ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದ ಜನರು ಮತದಾನ ಮಾಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

ಕೆಲವು ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾನಕ್ಕೆ ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಿರುವ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯು ಈ ಮುಂದಿನಂತಿದೆ.

ದೇಶಗಳು	ಮತದಾನಕ್ಕೆ ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಿರುವ ವಯೋಮಿತಿ
ಇಥಿಯೋಪಿಯಾ, ಈಕ್ವಿಡಾರ್, ಕ್ಯೂಬಾ, ಬ್ರೆಜಿಲ್, ಆಸ್ಟ್ರಿಯಾ	16
ಸೂಡಾನ್, ಸೌತ್ ಸೂಡಾನ್, ನಾರ್ತ್ ಕೊರಿಯಾ, ಇಂಡೋನೇಷಿಯಾ, ಗ್ರೀಸ್, ಈಸ್ಟ್ ಟಿಮೋರ್	17
ಆಸ್ಟ್ರೇಲಿಯಾ, ಚೀನಾ, ಬೆಲ್ಜಿಯಂ, ಆಫ್ಘಾನಿಸ್ತಾನ್, ಫಿನ್ ಲ್ಯಾಂಡ್, ಕೆನಡಾ, ಬಹಾಮಾಸ್, ಲೆಬನಾನ್, ಅಮೇರಿಕ, ಜಮೈಕಾ, ಇಸ್ರೇಲ್, ಜಿಂಬಾಬ್ವೆ, ಯೆಮನ್, ಕೀನ್ಯಾ, ಮೆಸಿಡೋನಿಯಾ, ಜಪಾನ್, ಇಟಲಿ, ಜೋರ್ಡಾನ್, ಮಂಗೋಲಿಯಾ, ಗುಟೆಮಾಲಾ, ತಾಂಜಾನಿಯಾ, ಡೆನ್ಮಾರ್ಕ್	18
ಸೌತ್ ಕೊರಿಯಾ	19
ತೈವಾನ್, ಬಹಾರೇನ್, ನೌರು	20

ಒಮೆನ್, ಸಿಂಗಾಪೂರ್, ಮಲೇಷಿಯಾ, ಕುವೈತ್, ಜೆರಿ, ಕ್ಯಾಮರೂನ್	21
ಯು.ಎ.ಇ.	25

ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ಮೂಲ: <http://www.worldatlas.com>

ಈ ರೀತಿ ವಿವಿಧ ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಮತದಾನ ಮಾಡಲು ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದರ ಮೂಲಕ ಆಯಾ ದೇಶದ ಜನರು ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.

2. ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಯಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ: ಮತದಾನ ಮಾಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವುದು ಒಂದು ವಿಧಾನವಾದರೆ, ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಯಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವುದು ಮತ್ತೊಂದು ವಿಧಾನವಾಗಿದೆ. ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ರಚನೆ ಮಾಡುವ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ದೇಶದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಪ್ರಜರಗಳಿಗೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಅದರಂತೆ ನಮ್ಮ ಸಂಸತ್ತಿನ ಕೆಳಮನೆಯಾದ ಲೋಕಸಭೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲು 25 ವರ್ಷ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಿದರೆ, ರಾಜ್ಯಸಭೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲು 30 ವರ್ಷ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಅದರಂತೆ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗದ ಕೆಳಮನೆಯಾದ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆಗೆ 25 ವರ್ಷ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಮೇಲ್ಮನೆಯಾದ ವಿಧಾನಪರಿಷತ್‌ಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲು 30 ವರ್ಷ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಅದರನ್ವಯ ಇಂದು ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಿರುವ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪೂರೈಸಿರುವ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

ವಿವಿಧ ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲು ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಿರುವ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಈ ಕೆಳಕಂಡ ಕೋಷ್ಟಕದಲ್ಲಿರುವಂತೆ ನೋಡಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

ದೇಶಗಳು	ಮೇಲ್ಮನೆ	ವಯೋಮಿತಿ	ಕೆಳಮನೆ	ವಯೋಮಿತಿ
ಆಸ್ಟ್ರೇಲಿಯ	ಸೆನೆಟ್	18	ಹೌಸ್ ಆಫ್ ರೆಪ್ರೆಸೆಂಟೇಟೀವ್ಸ್	18
ಆಸ್ಟ್ರಿಯ	ಫೆಡರಲ್ ಕೌನ್ಸಿಲ್	18	ನ್ಯಾಷನಲ್ ಕೌನ್ಸಿಲ್	18
ಬೆಲ್ಜಿಯಂ	ಸೆನೆಟ್	18	ಛೇಂಬರ್ ಆಫ್ ರೆಪ್ರೆಸೆಂಟೇಟೀವ್ಸ್	18
ಕೆನಡಾ	ಸೆನೆಟ್	30	ಹೌಸ್ ಆಫ್ ಕಾಮನ್ಸ್	21
ಫ್ರಾನ್ಸ್	ಸೆನೆಟ್	24	ನ್ಯಾಷನಲ್ ಅಸೆಂಬ್ಲಿ	18
ಇಂಡೋನೇಷಿಯ	ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿ ಮಂಡಳಿ	21	ನ್ಯಾಷನಲ್ ಅಸೆಂಬ್ಲಿ	21
ಜಪಾನ್	ಹೌಸ್ ಆಫ್ ಕೌನ್ಸಿಲರ್ಸ್	30	ಹೌಸ್ ಆಫ್ ರೆಪ್ರೆಸೆಂಟೇಟೀವ್ಸ್	25
ಫಿಲಿಪೈನ್ಸ್	ಸೆನೆಟ್	35	ಹೌಸ್ ಆಫ್ ರೆಪ್ರೆಸೆಂಟೇಟೀವ್ಸ್	25
ಸಿಂಗಾಪೂರ್	-----	-----	ಪಾರ್ಲಿಮೆಂಟ್ ಮೆಂಬರ್ಸ್	21
ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕೊರಿಯ	-----	-----	ನ್ಯಾಷನಲ್ ಅಸೆಂಬ್ಲಿ	18
ಸ್ವಿಡ್ಜರ್ಲ್ಯಾಂಡ್	ಕೌನ್ಸಿಲ್ ಆಫ್ ಸ್ಟೇಟ್ಸ್	18	ನ್ಯಾಷನಲ್ ಕೌನ್ಸಿಲ್	18
ಬ್ರಿಟನ್	ಶ್ರೀಮಂತರ ಸಭೆ	21	ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯರ ಸಭೆ	18
ಅಮೆರಿಕ	ಸೆನೆಟ್	30	ಹೌಸ್ ಆಫ್ ರೆಪ್ರೆಸೆಂಟೇಟೀವ್ಸ್	25
ಅರ್ಜೆಂಟೈನ್	ಸೆನೆಟ್	30	ಛೇಂಬರ್ ಆಫ್ ಡೆಪ್ಯುಟಿಸ್	25

ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ಮೂಲ: <https://www.pewresearch.org>

ಈ ರೀತಿ ವಿಶ್ವದ ಹಲವು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳು ಸಂಸತ್ತಿನ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಿ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಿವೆ.

4. ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಯುವ ಜನರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ:

ಭಾರತವು ಸಂಸದಿಯ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾಗಿದ್ದು ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳ ಮೂಲಕವೇ ಆಡಳಿತ ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಈ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಎಲ್ಲ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಹುದ್ದೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲು ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಅರ್ಹ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳಿಗೂ ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಜನರು ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿಸಿರುವಂತೆ 18 ವರ್ಷ ವಯೋಮಿತಿ ಪೂರೈಸಿದವರು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾನದ ಮೂಲಕ

ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿದರೆ 25 ವರ್ಷ ಮೇಲ್ಪಟ್ಟವರು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ವಯಸ್ಕರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಯುವಜನರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಎಂಬ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಯುವ ಜನರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ನೋಡುವುದಾದರೆ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಾಗಲಿ ಅಥವಾ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಯಾವುದೇ ಕಾಯಿದೆಯಲ್ಲಾಗಲಿ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ಯುವಜನರನ್ನು ಕುರಿತಂತೆ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟ ಚಿತ್ರಣವಿಲ್ಲ. ಅಂದರೆ ಯಾವ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯವರೆಗಿನವರನ್ನು ಯುವಜನರು ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯಬೇಕು ಎಂಬುದರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅಸ್ಪಷ್ಟತೆ ಇದೆ. ಆದಾಗ್ಯೂ ಸುಮಾರು 18 ವಯಸ್ಸಿನಿಂದ 45 ವಯಸ್ಸಿನವರೆಗಿನವರನ್ನು ಯುವ ಜನಾಂಗ ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಭಾರತ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಪಡೆದಾಗ ಇದ್ದ ಯುವಜನಾಂಗಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಅತಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಯುವಜನಾಂಗ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಈ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಯುವಜನರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ಪಡೆದಿದೆ. ಹಾಗಾದರೆ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಯುವಜನರು ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾವ ರೀತಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂಬ ಅಂಶವನ್ನು ಈ ಮುಂದಿನಂತೆ ನೋಡಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

4.1. ಹದಿನೆಂಟನೇ ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿದ ಯುವಜನರ ಅಂಕಿ ಅಂಶ:

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ 1952ರಿಂದ 2024ರವರೆಗೆ 18 ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ನಡೆದಿದ್ದು, ಈ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಯುವಜನರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗುತ್ತಲೇ ಇದೆ. ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಯಿಂದ 2024ರ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಅಂಕಿ ಅಂಶವನ್ನು ಮಾತ್ರ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಲಾಗಿದ್ದು ಅದರ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನಂತೆ ನೋಡಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಹದಿನೆಂಟನೇ ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯು ಏಪ್ರಿಲ್ 19ರಿಂದ ಜೂನ್ 1 ರವರೆಗೆ ಒಟ್ಟು 7 ಹಂತಗಳಲ್ಲಿ 543 ಸ್ಥಾನಗಳಿಗೆ ನಡೆಯಿತು. ಅದರ ಒಂದು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ನೋಡುವುದಾದರೆ,

ಹಂತಗಳು	ಚುನಾವಣಾ ದಿನಾಂಕ	ಒಟ್ಟು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳು	ಒಟ್ಟು ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳು	ಶೇಕಡಾವಾರು ಮತ ಚಲಾವಣೆ
ಮೊದಲನೇ ಹಂತ	19.04.2024	21	102	66.14%
ಎರಡನೇ ಹಂತ	26.04.2024	13	88	66.71%
ಮೂರನೇ ಹಂತ	07.05.2024	11	94	65.68%
ನಾಲ್ಕನೇ ಹಂತ	13.05.2024	10	96	69.16%
ಐದನೇ ಹಂತ	20.05.2024	8	49	62.2%
ಆರನೇ ಹಂತ	25.05.2024	8	58	63.37%
ಏಳನೇ ಹಂತ	01.05.2024	8	57	61.63%

ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ಮೂಲ: <https://eci.gov.in>

2024 ರ ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿದ್ದ ಮತದಾರರ ಅಂಕಿ ಅಂಶದ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಈ ಕೆಳಕಂಡಂತಿದೆ.

ಒಟ್ಟು ಮತದಾರರು	96.8 ಕೋಟಿ
ಪುರುಷ ಮತದಾರರು	49.7 ಕೋಟಿ
ಮಹಿಳಾ ಮತದಾರರು	47.1 ಕೋಟಿ
ತೃತೀಯ ಲಿಂಗಿ ಮತದಾರರು	48044 ಸಾವಿರ
ವಿಶೇಷ ಚೇತನ ಮತದಾರರು	88.35 ಲಕ್ಷ
18ರಿಂದ 19ವರ್ಷ ವಯಸ್ಸಿನ ಯುವ ಮತದಾರರು	1.85 ಕೋಟಿ

ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ಮೂಲ: <https://eci.gov.in>

ಹದಿನೆಂಟನೇ ಲೋಕಸಭೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿದ್ದ ಯುವರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳ ಬಗೆಗಿನ ಅಂಕಿ ಅಂಶ:

ಹದಿನೆಂಟನೇ ಲೋಕಸಭೆಯು ಏಪ್ರಿಲ್ 19, 2024 ರಿಂದ ಮೇ 01, 2024 ರವರೆಗೆ ಒಟ್ಟು ಏಳು ಹಂತಗಳಲ್ಲಿ 543 ಸದಸ್ಯ ಸ್ಥಾನಕ್ಕೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯು ನಡೆಯಿತು. ಈ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವಿಧ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳಿಂದ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳಿಂದ ಹಾಗೂ ಪಕ್ಷೇತರವಾಗಿ 8360 ಜನ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿದ್ದರು. ಇದರಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿದ್ದ ಬಹುತೇಕ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಸರಾಸರಿ 56 ವರ್ಷ ವಯಸ್ಸಿನವರು ಎಂಬುದು ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ ಸಂಗತಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಈ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅತಿ ಕಿರಿಯ ವಯಸ್ಸಿನ ನಾಲ್ಕು ಜನ ಸದಸ್ಯರು ಆಯ್ಕೆಯಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅವರುಗಳೆಂದರೆ,

ಹೆಸರು	ವಯಸ್ಸು	ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷ	ರಾಜ್ಯ / ಗೆದ್ದ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರ
ಪುಷ್ಪೇಂದ್ರ ಸರೋಜ್	25	ಸಮಾಜವಾದಿ	ಉತ್ತರ ಪ್ರದೇಶ/ ಕೌಶಂಬಿ
ಪ್ರಿಯಾ ಸರೋಜ್	25	ಸಮಾಜವಾದಿ	ಉತ್ತರ ಪ್ರದೇಶ/ಮಜ್ಜಿಶಹರ್
ಶಾಂಭವಿ ಚೌಧರಿ	26	ಲೋಕಜನಶಕ್ತಿ	ಬಿಹಾರ/ಸಮಷ್ಟಿಪರ
ಸಂಜನಾ ಜಾತವ್	25	ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್	ರಾಜಸ್ಥಾನ/ ಭರತ್‌ಪುರ

ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ಮೂಲ: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com>

ಈ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿದ್ದ ವಿವಿಧ ವಯಸ್ಸಿನ ಸದಸ್ಯರ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಈ ಕೆಳಕಂಡ ಪಟ್ಟಿಯ ಮೂಲಕ ನೋಡಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

ಸದಸ್ಯರ ವಯೋಮಿತಿ	ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ / %
25 ರಿಂದ 40 ವರ್ಷ	ಶೇ. 11%
41 ರಿಂದ 55 ವರ್ಷ	ಶೇ. 38%
55 ರಿಂದ 82 ವರ್ಷ	ಶೇ. 51%

ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ಮೂಲ: <https://eci.gov.in>

ಈ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ 2024ರ ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಆಯ್ಕೆಯಾದ ಸದಸ್ಯರ ಅಂಕಿ ಅಂಶವನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿದಾಗ ಬಹುತೇಕ ಯುವ ಜನಾಂಗದವರು ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಕ್ರಿಯವಾಗಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

5. ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಯುವಜನರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯಿಂದ ಕಾಣಬಹುದಾದ ನಿರೀಕ್ಷೆಗಳು:

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಯುವಜನರು ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾರರಾಗಿ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳಾಗಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಅವಕಾಶವಿದೆ. ಈ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಯುವ ಮತದಾರರ ಮೇಲೆ ನಿರೀಕ್ಷೆಗಳನ್ನು ಇಟ್ಟುಕೊಂಡಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಮತದಾರರು ಯುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ನಿರೀಕ್ಷೆ ಇಟ್ಟು ಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಯುವಜನರು ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿದಾಗ ಸಹಜವಾಗಿ ಕೆಲವೊಂದು ನಿರೀಕ್ಷೆಗಳನ್ನು ಇಟ್ಟುಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದು. ಅಂತಹ ಕೆಲವು ಅಂಶಗಳೆಂದರೆ,

1. **ಯುವರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳಿಂದ ಸರ್ಕಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೊಸತನ ಕಾಣುತ್ತದೆ:** ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಯುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿ ಗೆಲುವು ಸಾಧಿಸಿದಾಗ ಒಂದು ರೀತಿಯ ಹೊಸತನ ಕಂಡು ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಯಾಕೆಂದರೆ ಯುವಕರು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲರು ಮತ್ತು ಮಹತ್ವಾಕಾಂಕ್ಷಿವುಳ್ಳವರಾಗಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಯುವಜನರಿಂದ ಹೊಸ ಹೊಸ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಜನರು ನಿರೀಕ್ಷಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.
2. **ಯುವ ಮತದಾರರಿಂದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಗೆಲ್ಲುತ್ತವೆ ಎಂಬ ಆಸೆ ಇಟ್ಟಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ:** ಇಂದಿನ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿ ಯುವಜನರ ಮೇಲೆ ಭರವಸೆ ಇಟ್ಟಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಕಾರಣ ಯುವ ಮತದಾರರಿಗೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರವು ಹೊಸದಾಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಬೇಗ ಆಕರ್ಷಿತರಾಗುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಯುವಮತದಾರರಿಂದ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಮತವನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡು ಗೆಲ್ಲಬಹುದು ಎಂಬ ನಿರೀಕ್ಷೆ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಇರುತ್ತದೆ.
3. **ಸಂಸತ್ತಿನ ಕಾರ್ಯಕಲಾಪಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಕ್ರಿಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ:** ಯುವ ಜನಾಂಗದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿ ಗೆಲುವನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸಿದಾಗ ಸಂಸತ್ತಿನ ಕಾರ್ಯ ಕಲಾಪಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಕ್ರಿಯವಾಗಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ಲಭ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಜನರು ಯುವರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳಿಂದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಪೂರಕ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ ಎಂಬ ನಿರೀಕ್ಷೆ ಸಹಜವಾಗಿಯೇ ಇರುತ್ತದೆ.
4. **ಯುವಕರು ತಮ್ಮ ಹಕ್ಕನ್ನು ಕಳೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳದೆ ಕಡ್ಡಾಯವಾಗಿ ಮತ ಚಲಾಯಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ ಎಂಬ ಭಾವನೆ:** ಮತದಾನ ಎಂಬುದು ಎಲ್ಲ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳಿಗೂ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಕೊಟ್ಟಿರುವ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಹಕ್ಕಾಗಿದೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಹೊಸದಾಗಿ ಮತದಾರರ ಪಟ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸೇರ್ಪಡೆಗೊಂಡಿರುವ ಯುವಮತದಾರರು ಕಡ್ಡಾಯವಾಗಿ ತಮ್ಮ ಹಕ್ಕನ್ನು ಚಲಾಯಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ ಎಂಬ ನಿರೀಕ್ಷೆ ಇದೆ.
5. **ಯುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ವಲಯದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಶೀಘ್ರ ಸ್ಪಂದಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ ಎಂಬ ಆಕಾಂಕ್ಷೆ ಇದೆ:** ಯುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿದಾಗ ಮತ್ತು ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಪಡೆದಾಗ ಜನರಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದು ಆಶಾವಾದ ಇರುತ್ತದೆ. ಅದೇನೆಂದರೆ ಯುವರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲರಾಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಮತ್ತು ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನದ ಕೌಶಲ್ಯ ಹೊಂದಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸಿ ಶೀಘ್ರ ಪರಿಹಾರ ನೀಡುತ್ತಾರೆ ಎಂಬ ಭಾವನೆ ಜನಸಾಮಾನ್ಯರಲ್ಲಿರುತ್ತದೆ.

6. ಯುವ ಮತದಾರರು ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆ ಮಾಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಎಚ್ಚರಿಕೆ ನೀಡುತ್ತಾರೆ: ಯುವ ಮತದಾರರು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಬುದ್ಧಿವಂತರು ಮತ್ತು ಧೈರ್ಯವಂತರಾಗಿದ್ದು ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ನೇರವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆ ಮಾಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ಎಚ್ಚರಿಸುವ ಕೆಲಸವನ್ನು ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ ಎಂಬ ನಿರೀಕ್ಷೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವವರಿಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಸದಾ ಕಾಲ ಎಚ್ಚರಿಕೆಯಿಂದ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಈ ಮೇಲಿನ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಅಂಶಗಳು ಯುವಮತದಾರರು ಮತ್ತು ಯುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವುದರಿಂದ ಕಂಡು ಬರುವ ನಿರೀಕ್ಷೆಗಳಾಗಿವೆ.

6. ಯುವಜನರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕಂಡು ಬರುವ ಸವಾಲುಗಳು:

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಯುವಜನರು ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಕ್ರಿಯವಾಗಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಬೇಕೆಂಬ ಆಕಾಂಕ್ಷೆಗಳಿದ್ದರೂ ಸಹ ಕೆಲವೊಂದು ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅಂತಹ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಸವಾಲುಗಳೆಂದರೆ,

1. ಯುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ಅನಾನುಭವಿಗಳಾಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಸದನದ ಕಾರ್ಯಕಲಾಪದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಸಮರ್ಥರಾಗಿರುವುದಿಲ್ಲ: ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಯುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಅನುಭವದ ಕೊರತೆ ಇರುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಸಹಜವಾಗಿಯೇ ಅವರು ಸದನದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಾಜರಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಆದರೆ ಯಾವ ರೀತಿ ಚರ್ಚೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಬೇಕು ಎಂಬುದರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಆತಂಕ ಇರುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಯುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ಹಿರಿಯ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳಷ್ಟು ಸಮರ್ಥರಾಗಿರುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂಬುದು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.
2. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಯುವ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ: ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಹುಪಕ್ಷ ಪದ್ಧತಿ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಬಹುತೇಕ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಈ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಟಿಕೆಟ್ ನೀಡುವ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿಲೇ ಹಿಂದಿನಿಂದಲೂ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿದ್ದ ಹಿರಿಯ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಗೆಲ್ಲುವ ಸಾಧ್ಯತೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿರುವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಟಿಕೆಟ್ ನೀಡುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಯುವ ಜನರು ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗದಿರುವುದು ಒಂದು ಸವಾಲಾಗಿದೆ.
3. ಯುವ ಮತದಾರರು ಹಲವಾರು ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾನ ಮಾಡಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ಲಭ್ಯವಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ: ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಅರ್ಹ ಮತದಾರರು ಮತದಾನದ ದಿನದಂದು ಕಡ್ಡಾಯವಾಗಿ ಮತದಾನ ಮಾಡಲಿ ಎಂಬ ಕಾರಣಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ವೇತನ ಸಹಿತ ರಜಾ ದಿನದ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಇನ್ನಿತರ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಸಹ ಒದಗಿಸಿಕೊಟ್ಟಿದೆ. ಆದರೂ ಸಹ ಯುವ ಮತದಾರರು ಮತದಾರರ ಪಟ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ತಮ್ಮ ಹೆಸರನ್ನು ಸೇರ್ಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಕೆಲವು ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ದೋಷಗಳಿಂದಾಗಿ ಮತದಾರರ ಪಟ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ನೋಂದಾವಣೆ ಆಗಿರುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಮತದಾನದಿಂದ ವಂಚಿತರಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ.
4. ಯುವ ಮತದಾರರು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡುವಲ್ಲಿ ಗೊಂದಲಕ್ಕೆ ಒಳಗಾಗುತ್ತಾರೆ: ಯುವ ಮತದಾರರು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಭರವಸೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಹಿರಿಯ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಭಾಷಣಗಳ ಪ್ರಭಾವಕ್ಕೆ ಒಳಗಾಗುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇದರ ಪರಿಣಾಮದಿಂದಾಗಿ ಸೂಕ್ತ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡುವಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.
5. ಯುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ವಲಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಕಂಡು ಬರುವ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಪರಿಹಾರವನ್ನು ಕಂಡುಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಕಷ್ಟ: ಹೊಸದಾಗಿ ಆಯ್ಕೆಯಾದ ಯುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಕಂಡು ಬರುವ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಯಾವ ರೀತಿ ಪರಿಹರಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದು ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಶೀಘ್ರವಾಗಿ ಗುರುತಿಸುವುದು ಕಷ್ಟ. ಈ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಅವರು ಅನುದಾನಗಳನ್ನು ತರುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಗೊಳಿಸುವುದು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ.
6. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಿರಿಯ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳ ಜೊತೆ ಹೊಂದಾಣಿಕೆ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಕಷ್ಟ: ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರವೆಂಬುದು ಹಿರಿಯರ ಮತ್ತು ಕಿರಿಯರ ನಡುವೆ ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಿನ್ನಾಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಕಾರಣ ಹಿರಿಯ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ಅನುಭವಿಗಳಾಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಯುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಗಣನೆಗೆ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಹೀಗಾಗಿ ಹೊಂದಾಣಿಕೆ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಕಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಈ ಮೇಲಿನ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಅಂಶಗಳು ಯುವ ಮತದಾರರು ಮತ್ತು ಯುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ಸಹಜವಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಎದುರಿಸುವ ಸವಾಲುಗಳಾಗಿವೆ. ಇಂತಹ ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಸಮರ್ಥವಾಗಿ ಎದುರಿಸಿದಾಗ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಯುವಜನರು ಗಟ್ಟಿಯಾಗಿ ನೆಲೆಯೂರಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

7. ಉಪಸಂಹಾರ:

ಭಾರತವು ಯುವಜನರಿಂದ ಕೂಡಿದ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾಗಿದ್ದು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಸಾಧನೆ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿರುವುದನ್ನು ವಾಸ್ತವದಲ್ಲಿ ನೋಡಿದ್ದೇವೆ. ಇತ್ತೀಚಿನ ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಸತ್ತಿನ ಕೆಳಮನೆಯಾದ ಲೋಕಸಭೆಗೆ ಅತಿ ಕಿರಿಯ ವಯಸ್ಸಿನ ಸದಸ್ಯರು ಆಯ್ಕೆಯಾಗಿತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅದೇ ರೀತಿ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗದ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆಗೂ ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ಕಿರಿಯ ವಯಸ್ಸಿನ ಸದಸ್ಯರು ಆಯ್ಕೆಯಾಗಿ ಬರುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ

ಬಲವರ್ಧನೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವೆಂಬ ಮರ ಹೆಮ್ಮರವಾಗಿ ಬೆಳೆಯಲು ಯುವ ಜನರು ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಬೇಕು ಮತ್ತು ಯುವ ಮತದಾರರು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿ ಮತದಾನ ಮಾಡಿ ಸಮರ್ಥ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡಬೇಕು. ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆ ಯುವ ಜನಾಂಗ ಪ್ರತ್ಯಕ್ಷವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪರೋಕ್ಷವಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿದಾಗ ಮಾತ್ರ ಸದೃಢ ಭಾರತ ನಿರ್ಮಾಣ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

8. ಪರಾಮರ್ಶನ ಗ್ರಂಥಗಳು:

- ಡಾ. ರಾಜಶೇಖರ ಹೆಚ್. ಎಂ., (2001), ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ, ಕಿರಣ್ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ, ಮೈಸೂರು, (ಪು. 1 – 19)
- ಡಾ. ದುರ್ಗಾ ದಾಸ್ ಬಸು, (2015), ಇಂಟ್ರೋಡಕ್ಷನ್ ಟು ದ ಕಾನ್ಸ್ಟಿಟ್ಯೂಷನ್ ಆಫ್ ಇಂಡಿಯಾ, ಲೆಕ್ಚರ್ಸ್ ನೆಕ್ಸ್ಟ್ ಪಬ್ಲಿಕೇಷನ್ಸ್, ಹರಿಯಾಣ, (ಪು. 20-22)
- ಚರಣ್ ಲಾಲ್ ಸಾಹು, (2018), ಪ್ರೆಸಿಡೆಂಟ್ಸ್ ಆಫ್ ಇಂಡಿಯಾ ಆಂಡ್ ಅಮೇರಿಕ ವಿತ್ ಬ್ರಿಟನ್ಸ್ ಕಿಂಗ್ಡಂ & ಕ್ಲೇನ್ಸ್, ನೋಷನ್ ಪ್ರೆಸ್, ಚೆನ್ನೈ, (ಪು. 306)
- ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ರಚನಾ ಸಭೆಯ ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳು (ನಡವಳಿಗಳು) ಸಂಪುಟ 2, (2021), ಕನ್ನಡ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ ಇಲಾಖೆ ಮತ್ತು ಕುವೆಂಪು ಭಾಷಾ ಭಾರತಿ ಪ್ರಾಧಿಕಾರ, ಕಲಾಗ್ರಾಮ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು. (ಪು. 69-71)
- ಡಾ. ರಾಜಶೇಖರ ಹೆಚ್. ಎಂ., (2001), ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ, ಕಿರಣ್ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ, ಮೈಸೂರು, (ಪು. 41)
- <https://www.eci.com>
- <https://www.parliament.uk>
- Deccan Herald, 4th june

ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ವೈಪಲ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಪರ್ಯಾಯ: ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆ

ಡಾ. ವಿನುತಾ ಎಸ್ ಪಾಟೀಲ್

ಉಪನ್ಯಾಸಕರು

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ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಇದ್ದಂತಹ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವೂ ಒಂದು. ಈ ಮೂಲಕ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಜನರು ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ನೇರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ ತಮ್ಮ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆಗಳನ್ನು ತಾವೇ ಪೂರೈಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಸ್ವಯಂ ಆಡಳಿತವನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸಿಕೊಡುವ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನವಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಆದರೆ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಯು ಸ್ಥಾಪನೆಯಾದ ದಿನದಿಂದ ಇಲ್ಲಿಯವರೆಗೂ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿರುವ ಒಂದೇ ಆರೋಪವೆಂದರೆ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂಬುದು. ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳು ಹಲವಾರು ಕಾರಣಗಳನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸಿದೆ. ಆಡಳಿತ, ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಇವುಗಳು ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಗೆ ನೀಡದೇ ಇರುವುದರಿಂದಲೇ ಇಂದು ಅವುಗಳ ಸ್ಥಾಪನೆಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಪೂರ್ಣಗೊಂಡಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು. ಈ ಕುರಿತು ವಿವಿಧ ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳು ಗುರುತಿಸುವ ಕಾರಣಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಗೊಂದಲವಿರುವುದು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಾಗಾದರೆ ಈ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಗೆ ಪರ್ಯಾಯಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ವಿವರಣೆಗಳಿವೆಯೇ? ಈ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಲೇಖನವು ಮುಂದುವರೆಯುತ್ತದೆ.

ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಂವಿಧಾನವು ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅಧಿಕಾರ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳನ್ನಾಗಿ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಿಸಿದೆ. ಇದರರ್ಥ, 'ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯನ್ನು ಮಾಡಲು ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ, ಹಣಕಾಸಿನ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವಿಕಸನಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದುವುದೇ ಆಗಿದೆ'¹. ಆದರೆ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಸೂಕ್ತ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡದಿರುವುದು ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳ ವಿಫಲತೆಯ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಕಾರಣವೆಂದು ಬಹುಪಾಲು ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳು ಗುರುತಿಸಿವೆ. ಅವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ, ಮಣಿ ಶಂಕರ್ ಅಯ್ಯರ್ ಅವರ ಅಧ್ಯಕ್ಷತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಚನೆಯಾದಂತಹ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್‌ನ ಇಪ್ಪತ್ತನೇ ವಾರ್ಷಿಕೋತ್ಸವ ವರದಿ ನೀಡಿದ ವಿವರಣೆಯು ಈ ರೀತಿಯಾಗಿದೆ: "ವಿಫಲತೆಗೆ ಹಲವಾರು ಕಾರಣಗಳಿವೆ ಅವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾದವು, ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಚುನಾಯಿತ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳಿಗೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ನೀಡುವಲ್ಲಿ ಇರುವಂತಹ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಇಚ್ಛೆಯ ಕೊರತೆ, ನೌಕರ ವರ್ಗದ ಮೂಲಕ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡುವಲ್ಲಿ ಇರುವಂತಹ ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ ಇಚ್ಛೆಯ ಕೊರತೆ. ರಾಜ್ಯವು ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್‌ಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿರುವಂತಹ ಹುದ್ದೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸುವ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯ ಹೊಂದದೇ ಇರುವುದು. ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ನೌಕರರು ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡುವುದನ್ನು ವಿರೋಧಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದರೂ ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನದನ್ನು ಮಾಡುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರವಿಲ್ಲ" (Twentieth Anniversary Report of the expert committee on leveraging panchayats for efficient delivery of public goods and services vol-1. 2013: 78.).

¹ ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳು ಗುರುತಿಸಿರುವಂತೆ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ಎಂದರೆ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು ಹಣಕಾಸು ಹಾಗೂ ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಷಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರವಾಗಿರುವುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ರೀತಿಯ ಸ್ವಾಂತ್ರ್ಯದ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಿದೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳು ಗುರುತಿಸಿವೆ. (ನೋಡಿ, Overview of rural Decentralization in India. 2000. Vol-1. <http://www1.worldbank.org/publicsector/civilservice/june2004seminar/RuralDecent.pdf> 30/10/2017).

ಈ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖವು ತಿಳಿಸುವಂತೆ, ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣಾಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಲು ಅಗತ್ಯವಿರುವಂತಹ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಿಲ್ಲ. ಆ ಕಾರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಿಗೆ ನಿಯೋಜಿಸಿದ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತಮವಾಗಿ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ಈ ವರದಿಯು ವಿವರಿಸಿದೆ. ಹಾಗೂ ಈ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾರ್ಯ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಲು ಅಗತ್ಯ ಇರುವ ಸಿಬ್ಬಂದಿಗಳ ನೇಮಕವು ಕೂಡಾ ಈ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗೆ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗದೆ ಇರುವುದನ್ನು ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದಲ್ಲಿ ಗುರುತಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ವರದಿಯು ಗುರುತಿಸುವ ಇನ್ನೊಂದು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಅಂಶವೆಂದರೆ, “ಗ್ರಾಮ ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ನಿಜವಾದ ಅಧಿಕಾರಗಳಿಲ್ಲದೆ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸಭೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ತಮವಾದ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳು ಹಾಗೂ ಚುನಾಯಿತ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳು ಉತ್ತಮ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ. ಹಾಗೂ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸಭೆಗಳು ಸರಿಯಾಗಿ ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾಯಿತ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳು ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳು ಹೇಳಿದಂತೆ ಕೇಳುತ್ತಾರೆ ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಅಧಿಕಾರವಿದೆ” (ಅದೇ:548). ಹೀಗೆ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ನೀಡಿದ ಅಧಿಕಾರವು ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಣೆಗೆ ಸೂಕ್ತವಾಗಿಲ್ಲದ ಕಾರಣಕ್ಕಾಗಿಯೇ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸಭೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸರಿಯಾಗಿ ನಡೆಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ಈ ವರದಿಯು ಗುರುತಿಸಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸಭೆಯ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಕಾರ್ಯದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ 73 ನೇ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಯ 243 ನೇ ವಿಧಿಯು ಈ ರೀತಿಯಾಗಿ ವಿವರಿಸಿದೆ. “ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸಭೆಗೆ ಕಾನೂನಾತ್ಮಕವಾಗಿ ನೀಡಲ್ಪಟ್ಟ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳ ಅನ್ವಯ ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುವಂತೆ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗವಾಗಿ ಕೆಲಸಮಾಡಬಹುದು”².

ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸಭೆಯ ಮೂಲಕ ಆ ಗ್ರಾಮಕ್ಕೆ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿರುವ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳ ಕುರಿತಾದ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳನ್ನು ರಚಿಸುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸಭೆಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಮೂಲಕ ನಮಗೆ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗುವ ಅಂಶವೆಂದರೆ, ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯಿರುವುದು ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸಭೆಗೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡದೇ ಇರುವುದಲ್ಲ ಬದಲಾಗಿ ಅದನ್ನು ಸೂಕ್ತವಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗದೇ ಇರುವುದು. ಹಾಗೂ ಅಭಿಷೇಕ್ ಮಿತ್ರ ಅವರು ಪಶ್ಚಿಮ ಬಂಗಾಳದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ನಡೆಸಿ ಕಂಡುಕೊಂಡ ವಿಷಯವನ್ನು ಮಂಡಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅವರು ತಮ್ಮ ವಾದಕ್ಕೆ ಪೂರಕವಾಗುವಂತೆ ವಿವಿಧ ಚಿಂತಕರ ವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ವಿವರಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ನೈಲ್ ವೆಬ್ಸ್ಟರ್ ಅವರ ಟೀಕೆಯನ್ನು ಈ ರೀತಿಯಾಗಿ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

“ನೈಲ್ ವೆಬ್ಸ್ಟರ್ ಟೀಕೆಗೆ ಗುರಿಯಾಗುವಂತಹ ಎರಡು ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸಬಹುದು. ಮೊದಲನೆಯದು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ವಿಫಲತೆ. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಲು ಅಗತ್ಯವಿರುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಗ್ರಾಮ ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ನೀಡದೇ ಇರುವುದು ಹಾಗೂ ವಿವಿಧ ಇಲಾಖೆಗಳು ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಅವಶ್ಯಕ ಉಪಕರಣಗಳನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸದೇ ಇರುವುದು” (Nail Webster. 1992:78). ಹೀಗೆ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಸೂಕ್ತ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡದೇ ಇರುವುದರಿಂದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ. ಹಾಗೂ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವು ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ವಿಶ್ವಸಂಸ್ಥೆಯ ವರದಿಯು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. “ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವು ದುರ್ಬಲವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇತರ ದೇಶಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೋಲಿಸಿದಾಗ ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಅತಿ ಕೆಟ್ಟ ಪ್ರದರ್ಶನಕಾರರ ಪೈಕಿ ಭಾರತವು ಸೇರಿದೆ. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ನಿರ್ಣಯಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ ಕೈಯಲ್ಲಿದೆ. ...ಹಣಕಾಸಿನ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯು ದೋಷಪೂರಿತವಾಗಿದೆ. ಸಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಯಾಗಿ ಹತ್ತು ವರ್ಷಗಳಾದ ನಂತರವೂ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳ ಹಣಕಾಸು ಕಾರ್ಯಸೂಚಿ ಮತ್ತು ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನದ ಕುರಿತು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿಲ್ಲ” (World Bank. 2000: 22 and 25).

ಅಧಿಕಾರ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವನ್ನು ಶಾಸನಬದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಿದರೂ ಕೂಡಾ ಆಡಳಿತವು ಅಧಿಕಾರಶಾಹಿಗಳ ಕೈಯಲ್ಲಿ ಇದೆ. ಅಂದರೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರವು ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಮಟ್ಟದವರೆಗೂ ಹಂಚಿಕೆಯಾಗಿಲ್ಲ. ಹಾಗೂ ಹಣಕಾಸಿನ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಕುರಿತಾಗಿ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟತೆ ಇಲ್ಲ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಹೀಗೆ ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ ಮತ್ತು ಹಣಕಾಸಿನ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವು ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗಿಲ್ಲ. ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡದೇ ಇರುವುದು ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ತೊಡಕಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಹಣಕಾಸಿನ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನ ಕುರಿತಾಗಿ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟತೆಯಿಲ್ಲದ ಕಾರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಅದು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವು ಗುರುತಿಸಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಈ ವಾದಕ್ಕೆ ವೈರುಧ್ಯವನ್ನುಂಟು ಮಾಡುವ ಪುರಾವೆನ್ನು ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವೇ ಮುಂದಿನಂತೆ ನೀಡಿದೆ, ‘ಕೇರಳ ಮತ್ತು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ಆದಾಯ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ, ಯಾವುದೇ ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಇದು

² ಗ್ರಾಮ ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಯು ನಡೆಸುವ ಗ್ರಾಮಸಭೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಗ್ರಾಮದ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳಾಗಬೇಕು. ಈ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು ರಚನೆಯಾಗಬೇಕು. ಹೀಗೆ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸಭೆಯು ಪಂಚಾಯತ್‌ನ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗವಾಗಿ ಕೆಲಸಮಾಡಬೇಕು ಎಂದು ವಿವರಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. (ನೋಡಿ, The Constitution. Seventy-third Amendment Act. 1992(20th April, 1993). Part IX. Article 243-A. <https://bit.ly/2PeuaPL.05-12-19>).

ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿಲ್ಲ. ಹೀಗಾಗಿ ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆ ಎರಡೂ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ, ಸ್ವಂತ ಆದಾಯದ ಮೂಲವೂ ತೀರಾ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಇದೆ. 2001ರಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜ್ಯ ದೇಶೀಯ ಉತ್ಪನ್ನಕ್ಕೆ ಸ್ವಂತ ಮೂಲ ಆದಾಯದ ಅನುಪಾತವು ಕೇರಳದಲ್ಲಿ 0.1 ಪ್ರತಿಶತವಾದರೆ, ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಶತ 0.08ರಷ್ಟಿದೆ' (Document of world Bank. 2004: 8). ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವನ್ನು ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ ಸಾಧಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ವಿವರಿಸುವ ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳ ವಿವರಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಅಸಂಮಜಸತೆಯು ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆಯಾಗಿ ಈವರೆಗಿನ ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳು ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗಾಗಿಯೇ ಜಾರಿಗೆ ಬಂದಂತಹ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಯ ವಿಫಲತೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾದ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ವಿಫಲತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಈ ಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿನ ವಿರೋಧಾಭಾಸಗಳನ್ನು ಚರ್ಚಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಹಾಗೂ ಈ ಕಾರಣಗಳನ್ನಾಧರಿಸಿ, ನೀಡಲಾದ ಪರಿಹಾರಗಳ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನದ ನಂತರವೂ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳು ಮೂಲ ಸ್ವರೂಪದಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಇರುವುದನ್ನು ಇತ್ತೀಚಿನ ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಮೇಲಿನ ಕಾರಣಗಳಿಗಿಂತ ಮೂಲಭೂತವಾದ ಅಂಶಗಳ ಕಡೆಗೆ ಗಮನಹರಿಸುವ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿದೆ. ಅಂದರೆ ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳು ವಿಫಲತೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾದಂತಹ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟ ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಪರಿಹಾರಗಳ ಪಟ್ಟಿಯನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸುವ ಬದಲಾಗಿ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯನ್ನೇ ಸರಿಯಾಗಿ ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆಯಿದೆ. ಈ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ಬಿಡಿಸಲು ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿ ಅವರು ಗ್ರಾಮ ನಿರ್ವಹಣೆ ನೀಡಿದಂತಹ ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅವಲೋಕಿಸುವ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿದೆ. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿ ಅವರ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸ್ವರಾಜ್ಯ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತರಲಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಸರ್ವಸಮ್ಮತ. ಹಾಗಾದರೆ ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿ ಅವರು ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ಎಂದರೆ ಯಾವ ಅರ್ಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ? ಈ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಂದುವರೆಯೋಣ.

ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿ ಅವರ ಪರ್ಯಾಯ ಸ್ವಾಯತ್ತ ಘಟಕ

ಈ ಮೇಲಿನ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ಎಂದರೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವಿವಿಧ ಹಂತಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹಂಚುವುದು ಎಂಬರ್ಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿ ಅವರು ಇದಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಭಿನ್ನವಾಗಿ ಬಳಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇದರ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಈ ಮುಂದಿನಂತೆ ವಿವರಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ, ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿಯವರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ನಿಜವಾದ ಭಾರತವು ನಗರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಇಲ್ಲ. ಅದು ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಸಿದೆ. ಭಾರತವು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯಾಗಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರವು ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತಗೊಳ್ಳದೇ ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಸಿರಬೇಕು ಎನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ 'ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಅಹಿಂಸಾತ್ಮಕ ಸಮಾಜ ರಚನೆ ಹೊಂದಿರುವುದಿಲ್ಲ' (ಗಾಂಧಿ. 1942: 320). ಅಂದರೆ "ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತ ಹಾಗೂ ಸಂಘಟಿತ ರೂಪದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಿಂಸೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗೆ ಆತ್ಮ ಎಂಬುದಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಆತ್ಮವೇ ಇಲ್ಲದ ಯಂತ್ರದಂತಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಅದು ತನ್ನ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಋಣಿಯಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಹಿಂಸೆಯಿಂದ ತಪ್ಪಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲಾರದು. ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಬಲವನ್ನು ಆಧರಿಸಿರುವ ಸಂಘಟನೆಯನ್ನು ನಾನು ಅಂಗೀಕರಿಸುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಬದಲಾಗಿ ಸ್ವಯಂಪ್ರೇರಿತ ಸಂಘಟನೆ ಇರಬೇಕು" (ಗಾಂಧಿ. 2015: 90).

ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿಯವರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ನಿಜವಾದ ಭಾರತವು ನಗರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಇಲ್ಲ. ಅದು ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಸಿದೆ. ಭಾರತವು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯಾಗಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರವು ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತಗೊಳ್ಳದೇ ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಸಿರಬೇಕು ಎನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ 'ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಅಹಿಂಸಾತ್ಮಕ ಸಮಾಜ ರಚನೆ ಹೊಂದಿರುವುದಿಲ್ಲ' (ಗಾಂಧಿ. 1942: 320). ಅಂದರೆ "ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತ ಹಾಗೂ ಸಂಘಟಿತ ರೂಪದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಿಂಸೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗೆ ಆತ್ಮ ಎಂಬುದಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಆತ್ಮವೇ ಇಲ್ಲದ ಯಂತ್ರದಂತಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಅದು ತನ್ನ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಋಣಿಯಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಹಿಂಸೆಯಿಂದ ತಪ್ಪಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲಾರದು. ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಬಲವನ್ನು ಆಧರಿಸಿರುವ ಸಂಘಟನೆಯನ್ನು ನಾನು ಅಂಗೀಕರಿಸುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಬದಲಾಗಿ ಸ್ವಯಂಪ್ರೇರಿತ ಸಂಘಟನೆ ಇರಬೇಕು" (ಗಾಂಧಿ. 2015: 90). ಆದ್ದರಿಂದಲೇ ಇಂದು ದೊಡ್ಡ ದೊಡ್ಡ ನಗರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತವಾದಂಥ ಅಧಿಕಾರವು ಹಳ್ಳಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಸಬೇಕು ಎಂಬುದು ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿಯವರ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯ. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸುಮಾರು ಏಳು ಲಕ್ಷ ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳು ಇದ್ದು ಗ್ರಾಮದ ಜನರ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಬಗೆಹರಿಸಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅವರ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪೂರೈಸಬೇಕಾದರೆ ನಾವು ಅವುಗಳಿಗೆ ಸ್ವಾಯತ್ತತೆ ನೀಡಬೇಕು. ಮೂಲಕ ಗ್ರಾಮದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಗ್ರಾಮದ ಜನರೇ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡಬೇಕು ಎಂಬುದು ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿಯವರ ಚಿಂತನೆಯಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಅದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿಯವರು 'ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸ್ವರಾಜ್ಯ' ಎಂಬ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯನ್ನೇ ಹುಟ್ಟುಹಾಕಿದರು. ಹಾಗೆ 'ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸ್ವರಾಜ್ಯ' ಯಾವ ರೀತಿ ಇರಬೇಕು ಎಂಬುದರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ತಮ್ಮ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯನ್ನು ವಿವರಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. "ನನ್ನ ಕಲ್ಪನೆಯ ಗ್ರಾಮಸ್ವರಾಜ್ಯ ಎಂದರೆ ಅದು ಒಂದು ಪರಿಪೂರ್ಣ ಪ್ರಜಾರಾಜ್ಯ. ತನ್ನ ಜೀವನಾವಶ್ಯಕತೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅದು ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ. ಸ್ವಾವಲಂಬನೆ ಅದರ ಆಧಾರ. ಅಗತ್ಯವಾಗುವಕಡೆಗಳೆಲ್ಲ ಗ್ರಾಮಗ್ರಾಮಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ಪರಸ್ಪರಾವಲಂಬನೆ ಇದ್ದೇ ಇರುತ್ತದೆ. ಆಹಾರಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಬೆಳೆ, ಬಟ್ಟೆಗಾಗಿ ಹತ್ತಿ ಬೆಳೆಯುವುದು ಪ್ರಥಮ ಲಕ್ಷ್ಯ. ದನಕರುಗಳಿಗಾಗಿ ಕಾವಲು, ಮಕ್ಕಳಿಗೆ ಆಟದ ಬಯಲು, ಮನರಂಜನೆಗಾಗಿ ಸ್ಥಳ ಇವುಗಳಿಗಾಗಿ ಜಮೀನು ಮೀಸಲಾಗಿರಬೇಕು. ಇಷ್ಟು ಪೂರೈಸಿದ ನಂತರವೇ ಹಣಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಬೆಳೆಯುವ ಬೆಳೆಗಳು, ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಗಾಂಜಾ ತಂಬಾಕು ಆಫೀಮು ನಿಷಿದ್ಧ. ಹಳ್ಳಿಹಳ್ಳಿಯಲ್ಲೂ ಸಭಾಂಗಣ, ರಂಗಮಂದಿರ, ಶಾಲೆ, ಶುದ್ಧ ನೀರಿನ ಪೂರೈಕೆ, ಮೂಲ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಎಲ್ಲರಿಗೂ ಕಡ್ಡಾಯ. ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾದಮಟ್ಟಿಗೂ ಗ್ರಾಮದ ವ್ಯವಹಾರವೆಲ್ಲಕ್ಕೂ ಸಹಕಾರ ತತ್ವವೇ ಆಧಾರ. ಅಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿಬೇಧವಿರದು. ಸತ್ಯಾಗ್ರಹ ಮತ್ತು ಅಸಹಕಾರ

ತತ್ವವೇ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸ್ವರಾಜ್ಯದ ಆಧಾರ ಶಕ್ತಿ ಯೋಗ್ಯವಾದ ಕನಿಷ್ಠ ಅರ್ಹತೆಯುಳ್ಳ ಎಲ್ಲ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಪುರುಷರೂ ವರ್ಷಕ್ಕೆ ಒಮ್ಮೆ ಚುನಾಯಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಐವರ ಪಂಚಾಯತಿ ಹಳ್ಳಿಯ ಆಡಳಿತವನ್ನು ನಡೆಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ. ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ಬೇಕಾದ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಮತ್ತು ನಿಯಮಗಳು ಈ ಮಂಡಳಿಗೆ ಇರುತ್ತವೆ. ಈಗಿನ ರೀತಿಯ ನ್ಯಾಯವಿತರಣೆಯ ಬದಲು ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಯೇ ತನ್ನ ಅಧಿಕಾರಾವಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗ, ಕಾರ್ಯಾಂಗ ಮತ್ತು ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗವಾಗಿ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯದ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಪರಿಪೂರ್ಣ ಜನತಂತ್ರ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನದಲ್ಲಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಅಹಿಂಸೆಯ ನಿಯಮಗಳೇ ಕಟ್ಟಳೆ. ಅವನೂ, ಅವನ ಗ್ರಾಮವೂ ಇಡೀ ಲೋಕದ ಶಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಬೇಕದರೆ ಎದುರಿಸಲು ಶಕ್ತರಾಗುತ್ತಾರೆ” (ಗಾಂಧಿ. 2001: 18 ಮತ್ತು 20). ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿಯವರು ಮೇಲೆ ಹೇಳಿದಂತೆ, ಮುಕ್ತವೂ, ಸ್ವಚ್ಛವೂ ಸತ್ಯಾಧಾರಿತವೂ ಆದ ಸರಳ ಸುಂದರ ಸಮೃದ್ಧ ಗ್ರಾಮಸ್ವರಾಜ್ಯವನ್ನು ಬಯಸಿದರು. ಅವರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ “ಹಳ್ಳಿಯ ಜೀವನ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯ ಪುನರುತ್ಥಾನವೇ ನಿಜವಾದ ಸ್ವರಾಜ್ಯ. ಭಾರತದ ಜೀವ-ಜೀವಾಳ ಕೃತಕ ನಗರ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯಿಂದ ಎಂದೂ ಪೋಷಿತವಾಗದು. ಅದರ ಅಸಂಖ್ಯಾತ ಹಳ್ಳಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪಸರಿಸಿ ನಿಲ್ಲುವಂಥ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರಿತ, ವಿಜ್ಞಾನಾಧಾರಿತ, ವಿಶ್ವಾಸವರ್ಧಕ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸ್ವರಾಜ್ಯ ಸ್ಥಾಪನೆಯಿಂದ ಮಾತ್ರ ಪ್ರಗತಿ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುವುದರಿಂದ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಜೀವನದ ಮೂಲಾಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಪುನರ್ ಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠಾಪನೆಗೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು ಎನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ” (ಗಾಂಧಿ. 2001: 5).

ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಹಾಗೂ ಔದ್ಯೋಗಿಕ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ವದೇಶಿ ತತ್ವವನ್ನು ಕೈ ಬಿಟ್ಟಿರುವುದರಿಂದಲೇ ನಮ್ಮ ಜನಸೋಮಕ್ಕೆ ಕಡುಬಡತನ ಒದಗಿದೆ ಎನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಹಿಂಸೆ ತತ್ವವನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡರೆ ಬಡತನ, ನಿರುದ್ಯೋಗ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಯಂತಹ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳು ಪರಿಹಾರವಾಗುವುದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಸ್ವಾವಲಂಬನೆ ಹೊಂದಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಎನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿಯವರು ಅಹಿಂಸೆ ತತ್ವವನ್ನು ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯಿಂದ ಸಮಷ್ಟಿಗೆ ವಿಸ್ತರಿಸುವುದರ ಮೂಲಕ ರಾಜಕೀಯ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಂಗದಲ್ಲೂ ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದು ಎಂದು ವಾದಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. “ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿ ಹೇಳಿದ ಹಾಗೆ ಅಗಾಧ ಪ್ರಮಾಣದ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆ (Mass production) ಬಡಜನತೆಗೆ ನೆರವಾಗದು. ಅವರ ಅಭಿಕ್ರಮ ಶಕ್ತಿಗೆ ಚಾಲನೆ ನೀಡಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಪೋಷಿಸದು. ಬೃಹತ್ ವ್ಯಾಪಾರೀ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ತಂತ್ರವಿನ್ಯಾಸದ ಒಡಲಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಹಿಂಸೆ ನಿಸರ್ಗನಾಶ, ಶಕ್ತಿ ಮೂಲಗಳ ದುಂದು ಬಳಕೆ, ಕ್ಷಿಪ್ರ ಕ್ಷಾಮ-ಡಾಮರಗಳು ತುಂಬಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಅವು ಮಾನವನ ಶೋಷಣೆಯನ್ನು ನಿರಂತರವೂ ಮಾಡುತ್ತವೆ. ಹಳ್ಳಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸರಳ ಸಾಧನಗಳಿಂದ ಉತ್ಪಾದಿಸಿ ಬೃಹತ್ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಸಂಕೋಲೆಗಳಿಂದ ಮುಕ್ತವಾದ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತ ಆಧುನಿಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಸಾಧ್ಯ. ಅಂತಹ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸಮಾಜ ಬಡತನ ನಿರುದ್ಯೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ನಿವಾರಿಸಲು ಶಕ್ಯವಾದೀತು” (ಗಾಂಧಿ. 2001: 11 ಮತ್ತು 12).

ಹಳ್ಳಿಯ ಬಡಗಿ ಕಮಾರರಿಗೆ ಕೆಲಸ ಸಿಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಎತ್ತುಗಳಿಗೆ ಮೇವು ಮತ್ತು ಗೊಬ್ಬರಕ್ಕೆ ಸೊಗೆ, ಬೆಂಡು, ಸಿಪ್ಪೆಗಳ ಉಪಯೋಗ ಪಡೆಯಬಹುದು. ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಯಿಂದ ಬೆಲ್ಲ ಉತ್ತಮ, ಸಕ್ಕರೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಸಾಯನಿಕಗಳ ಬಳಸುವುದರಿಂದ ಪುಷ್ಟಿಕರ ಲವಣಗಳು ನಾಶವಾಗುತ್ತವೆ. ಆರ್ಥಿಕವಾಗಿ ಕಬ್ಬಿನ ಸಾಗಾಣಿಕೆಯ ವೆಚ್ಚ ಮತ್ತು ಶ್ರಮ ಉಳಿತಾಯ. ಹಾಗೂ ರೈತ ತನ್ನ ಬೆಳೆಗೆ ತಾನೇ ಒಡೆಯನಾಗಿರುತ್ತಾನೆ. ಪರಿಸರ ಮಾಲಿನ್ಯಕರಣವೂ ಕಡಿಮೆ. ಈ ಕಾರಣಗಳಿಂದಲೇ ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿಯವರು ಗುಡಿ ಕೈಗಾರಿಕೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಒತ್ತು ಕೊಟ್ಟಿರುವುದು.

ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಯಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಗಿರಣಿಗಳು ಕಡೆಯಪಕ್ಷ ಹತ್ತು ಮಂದಿಯ ಕೆಲಸವನ್ನು ಕಿತ್ತು ಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿವೆ. “ಕೆಲಸಕ್ಕೆ ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ದುಡಿಯುವ ಕೈಗಳು ಇಲ್ಲದಿರುವಾಗ, ಯಾಂತ್ರಿಕರಣ ಒಳ್ಳೆಯದೇ, ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ, ಕೆಲಸಕ್ಕಿಂತ ದುಡಿಯುವ ಕೈಗಳೇ ಜಾಸ್ತಿಯಾದಾಗ, ಯಂತ್ರ ಒಂದು ಪಿಡುಗು. ಅದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ನಾವು ಹಳ್ಳಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಉದ್ಯೋಗವನ್ನು ಕೊಂಡೊಯ್ಯಬೇಕಾದ್ದು ಯಂತ್ರದ ಮೂಲಕ ಅಲ್ಲ. ಅವರು ಇದುವರೆಗೂ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದ ಕಸಬುಗಳನ್ನು ಪುನರುಜ್ಜೀವಿಸುವುದರ ಮೂಲಕ. ಅಂದರೆ ಸತ್ತು ಹೋಗುತ್ತಿರುವ ಅಥವಾ ಹೋಗಿರುವ ಗ್ರಾಮೋದ್ಯೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ಎಲ್ಲೆಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಧ್ಯವೋ, ಎಲ್ಲೆಲ್ಲಿ ಅಪೇಕ್ಷಿತವೋ ಅಲ್ಲೆಲ್ಲ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲೇ ಪುನಶ್ಚೇತನಗೊಳಿಸುವುದು” (ಗಾಂಧಿ. 1934: 316). ಯಾಂತ್ರಿಕರಣ ಗ್ರಾಮದ ಆರ್ಥಿಕತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಉದ್ಯೋಗಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಪರಿಣಾಮ ಬೀರುವುದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಜನರ ಆರೋಗ್ಯದ ಮೇಲೂ ಪರಿಣಾಮ ಬೀರುತ್ತಿದೆ. ‘ಭತ್ತದ ಗಿರಣಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಹಿಟ್ಟಿನ ಗಿರಣಿಗಳು ಸಾವಿರಾರು ಬಡ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಶ್ರಮಿಕರ ಸ್ಥಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಆಕ್ರಮಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದಲ್ಲದೇ ಇಡೀ ಜನಸಮುದಾಯದ ಆರೋಗ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಕೂಡಾ ಹಾನಿಯನ್ನುಂಟು ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿವೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿಯವರ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯ. ಈ ಗಿರಣಿಗಳಿಂದ ಗೋಧಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಪಾಲಿಷ್ ಮಾಡದ ಅಕ್ಕಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ದೊರೆಯಬಹುದಾದ ಪುಷ್ಟಿದಾಯಕ ಮತ್ತು ಜೀವಧಾರಕ ಧಾತುಗಳನ್ನು ಕಸಿದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದರ ಮೂಲಕ ಭಾರತೀಯರ ಆರೋಗ್ಯದ ಮೇಲೆ ಪ್ರತಿಕೂಲ ಪರಿಣಾಮ ಉಂಟಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ’ (ಅದೇ: 316). ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿಯವರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಮೂಲ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ನೀಡಬೇಕು ಎನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ, ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿ ಅವರ ಮೂಲ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣವು, ಕುಶಲ ಕೈಕೆಲಸ, ಕಲೆ, ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಎಲ್ಲವನ್ನು ಒಂದೇ ಯೋಜನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮೇಳೈಸಬೇಕು. ಈ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಎಲ್ಲರಿಗೂ ಸುಲಭವಾಗಿ ಸಿಗುವಂತಾದರೆ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ಹಳ್ಳಿಯವನಿಗೂ ನಿತ್ಯ ಜೀವನಕ್ಕೆ ಉಪಯುಕ್ತವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಎನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಈ ಮೇಲಿನ ಸ್ವದೇಶಿ ತತ್ವಗಳನ್ನು ದೇಶಪ್ರೇಮಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಅನುಸರಿಸದೇ ಒಂದು ವ್ರತದಂತೆ ಪಾಲಿಸಬೇಕು ಎಂಬುದು ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿ ಅವರ ವಾದವಾಗಿದೆ (ಗಾಂಧಿ. 2001: 306). ಸ್ವದೇಶಿ ತತ್ವವನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸುವುದರಿಂದ ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳು ಸ್ವಯಂಪರಿಪೂರ್ಣತೆಯನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆಯಾಗಿ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ವಿಫಲತೆಯೊಂದೇ ಅಲ್ಲದೇ ಇದರ ಪರ್ಯಾಯ ಯೋಜನೆಯ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಈ ಮೇಲಿನ ವಿವರಣೆಯಿಂದ ತಿಳಿದುಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಹಂಚುವುದನ್ನು ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ಎಂದು ವಿವರಿಸಬಹುದು. ಆದರೆ ಈ ಮೂಲಕ ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಿಲ್ಲ ಬದಲಾಗಿ ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳು ಸ್ವಾಯತ್ತ ಘಟಕಗಳಾಗಿರಬೇಕು ಎಂದು ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿ ಅವರು ವಿವರಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇವರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ, ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳು ಸ್ವಯಂಪೂರ್ಣತೆಯಿಂದ ಕೂಡದೆ ಹೋದರೆ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಹೊಂದಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಿಲ್ಲ ಎನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಒಂದು ಗ್ರಾಮವು ಆಡಳಿತ, ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಜೀವನ, ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಮತ್ತು ಭದ್ರತೆ ಸೇರಿದಂತೆ ಗ್ರಾಮದ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಸ್ವಯಂಪರಿಪೂರ್ಣತೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರಬೇಕು. ಈ ಸ್ವಯಂ ಪರಿಪೂರ್ಣತೆಯನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಗ್ರಾಮವು ಸ್ವಾಯತ್ತ ಘಟಕವಾಗಿರಬೇಕು ಎನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಗಾಂಧೀಜಿ ಅವರು ವಿವರಿಸುವ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ತತ್ವವನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆ ಇದೆ. ಈ ಕುರಿತಾದ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಈ ಲೇಖನ ತೆರೆದಿಡುತ್ತದೆ.

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ಪರಿಚಯ;

ನರಸಿಂಹ ರಾಜು ಹೆಗ್ಡೆರೆ,

ಸುಫಿಯಾ ಕಾನೂನು ಕಾಲೇಜು, ತುಮಕೂರು-572102. ಮೊ: 9964898726.

ಪುಲಿ ಮಂಜುನಾಥ ಜೋಗಿ

ಪ್ರಾಧ್ಯಾಪಕರು, ಸ.ಪ್ರ.ದ.ಕಾಲೇಜು, ಕೊರಟಗೆರೆ

:- ಮಾರ್ಗದರ್ಶಕರು :-

ಪುಲಿ ಮಂಜುನಾಥ ಜೋಗಿ

ಎಂ.ಎ. ಎಂಫಿಲ್,

ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಉಪನ್ಯಾಸಕರು, ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಪ್ರಥಮ ದರ್ಜೆ ಕಾಲೇಜು, ಕೊರಟಗೆರೆ, ತುಮಕೂರು. ಮೊ : 9110236286.

ಭಾರತದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಹಾಗೂ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಪರಿಸರದ ಸ್ಥಿತಿ-ಗತಿ-ಲಯಗಳು ಇಲ್ಲಿನ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಏಳು-ಬೀಳಿನ ಮೇಲೆ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಿತವಾಗುತ್ತವೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಭಾರತದ ಜಾತಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯವನ್ನು ಸಮಗ್ರವಾಗಿ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡಬೇಕಾದುದು ಇಂದಿನ ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಾದ ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರೀಯ ಕಾರ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಅನಾದಿ ಕಾಲದಿಂದಲೂ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಹುಟ್ಟಿ ಬೆಳೆದು ಬೇರು ಬಿಟ್ಟಿರುವ ಜಾತಿ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯು ರಾಜಕೀಯದೊಡನೆ ಬೇರ್ಪಡಿಸಲಾಗದಂತೆ ಬೆಸೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದೆ. ರಾಜ್ಯ ರಾಜಕಾರಣವೇ ಆಗಲಿ ಅಥವಾ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜಕಾರಣವೇ ಆಗಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಹಣೆಬರಹವೆಂಬುದು ತೀರ್ಮಾನಿತವಾಗುವುದು ಇದೇ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದ ಮೇಲೆಯೇ ಆಗಿದೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ, ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳೇ ಆಗಲಿ, ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳೇ ಆಗಲಿ ಅವರ ಪ್ರಥಮ ಆದ್ಯತೆ ಬಹು ಸಂಖ್ಯಾತ ಜಾತಿಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಓಲೈಕೆಯೇ ಆಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಎಲ್ಲರ ಅರಿವಿಗೆ ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ಸಮಾವೇಶಗಳು ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಅತ್ಯುತ್ತಮ ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗಳಾಗಿ ನಮ್ಮ ಮುಂದಿವೆ. ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಪಕ್ಷವೂ ಜಾತಿ ಸಮಾವೇಶ ನಡೆಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿಯ ಮತಗಳ ಓಲೈಕೆಗೆ ಮುಂದಾಗುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇದೇ ಮಾದರಿಯನ್ನೇ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳೂ ಅನುಸರಿಸುವುದು ವಾಡಿಕೆಯಾಗಿದೆ.

ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳ ಓಲೈಕೆಗೂ ಸಹ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಮುಂದಾಗುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಇತ್ತೀಚಿನ ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಆತಂಕದ ವಾತಾವರಣವನ್ನು ಭಾರತದಾದ್ಯಂತ ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಸಮುದಾಯ - ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ಸಾಮರಸ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಬದಲಾಗಿ ಬಿಗುವಿನ ವಾತಾವರಣ ನಿರ್ಮಾಣಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಈ ಸಮುದಾಯ ಕೇಂದ್ರಿತ ರಾಜಕಾರಣವು ಮುಂದೊಂದು ದಿನ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ "ಫ್ಯಾಸಿಸ್ಟ್" ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಹುಟ್ಟು ಹಾಕಬಹುದೆಂಬ ಆತಂಕವು ಪ್ರಜ್ಞಾವಂತರಲ್ಲಿದೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಬಹುದಾದ ಸನ್ನಿವೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ನಿವಾರಿಸುವ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನೇತಾರರು ಶ್ರಮಿಸಬೇಕಿರುವುದು ಇಂದಿನ ತುರ್ತು ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆಯಾಗಿದೆ.

ಜಾತಿಯ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಯಿತೇ ಭಾರತದ ಪುರಾತನ ರಾಜಕೀಯ?

ದೇಶದ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ಇಲ್ಲಿನ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಗೆ ತಕ್ಕಂತೆ ಬೆಳೆದು ಬಂದಿರುವುದು ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಇತಿಹಾಸವನ್ನು ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡಿದಾಗ ಕಂಡುಬರುವ ಸತ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಆರಂಭಿಕ ದಿನಮಾನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವೃತ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಆಧರಿಸಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು, ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯ ಕುಟುಂಬವನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸುವುದು ಸರ್ವೇ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಮಡಕೆ ತಯಾರಿಸುವ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡುವವನನ್ನು ಕುಂಬಾರನೆಂದು, ಕುರಿ ಕಾಯುವ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡುವವನನ್ನು ಕುರುಬ ಎಂದು, ಹೊಲಿಗೆ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡುವವನನ್ನು ಚಿಂಪಿಗನೆಂದು, ಬಟ್ಟೆ ಒಗೆಯುವ ಕಾರ್ಯಮಾಡುವವನನ್ನು ಮಡಿವಾಳನೆಂದು, ಹೀಗೆ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯ ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿದ್ದ ವೃತ್ತಿಯೇ ಅವನ ಜಾತಿಯಾಗಿ ಆತನನ್ನು ಬಿಡದೇ ಅಂಟಿಕೊಂಡಿದೆ.

ಸಮಾಜದ ಮುಂದುವರಿಕೆಗಾಗಿ, ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಕಾರ್ಯ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸಕ್ರಿಯಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಸಲುವಾಗಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಪಟ್ಟಭದ್ರ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಗಳ ರಕ್ಷಣೆಗಾಗಿ ಜಾತಿಯನ್ನು ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳ ಕೊರಳಿಗೆ ನೇತುಹಾಕಲಾಯಿತು. ಅಷ್ಟೇ ಅಲ್ಲದೇ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯು ಇಚ್ಛಿಸಿದರೂ ತನ್ನ ಜಾತಿ ಸಂಕೋಲೆಗಳಿಂದ ಹೊರಬರಲಾರದಂತಹ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ವಾತಾವರಣವನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸಿರುವುದೂ ಸಹ ಇದೇ ಪಟ್ಟಭದ್ರ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯವೇ ಆಗಿದೆ. ಚಪ್ಪಲಿ ಹೊಲಿಯುವ ಚಮ್ಮಾರನು ತನಗೆ ಇಷ್ಟವಿಲ್ಲ ಈ ಕಸುಬು ಹಾಗೂ ಈ ಅಣೆ ಪಟ್ಟಿ ಎಂದು ಅದರಿಂದ ಹೊರಬರಲು ಸಮಾಜದ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ಅವನನ್ನು ಅನುಮತಿಸುವುದಿಲ್ಲ.

ಯಾವ ಪಟ್ಟಭದ್ರ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ಜಾತಿ ಪದ್ಧತಿಗೆ ಜನ್ಮ ನೀಡಿತೋ ಅದೇ ಪಟ್ಟಭದ್ರ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಜಾತಿಪದ್ಧತಿಯನ್ನು ಮುಂದುವರಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಹೋಗುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಚಳುವಳಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಿಂದ ಕೊಡಮಾಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿರುವ ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳ ಕಾರಣದಿಂದಾಗಿ ಒಂದಷ್ಟು ರಕ್ಷಣೆ ದೊರೆತಿದೆ ಬಿಟ್ಟರೆ ಜಾತಿಯ ಬೇರು ಭೂಗರ್ಭದವರೆಗೂ ವ್ಯಾಪಿಸಿರುವುದು ಸುಳ್ಳಲ್ಲ.

ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಅದರ ಹಿಂದಿರುವ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳು :

ಪ್ರಸಕ್ತ ಭಾರತದ ಸನ್ನಿವೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ತನ್ನ ವಿರಾಟ ರೂಪವನ್ನು ಧರಿಸಿರುವುದು ನಿಚ್ಚಳವಾಗಿದೆ. ಅದರ ಹಿಂದಿನ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಲೆಕ್ಕಾಚಾರಗಳು ಅರ್ಥವಾಗದೇ ಇರುವಂತಹ ಲೆಕ್ಕಾಚಾರಗಳೇನೂ ಅಲ್ಲ. ಜಾತಿಗೊಂದರಂತೆ ಮಠಗಳ ಸ್ಥಾಪನೆ, ಜಾತಿ ಸಮಾವೇಶಗಳು, ಜಾತಿಗೆ ಸಂಭಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಅನುದಾನಗಳ ಘೋಷಣೆ ಹೀಗೆ ಜಾತಿ ರಾಜಕಾರಣ ಒಂದೆಡೆಯಾದರೆ, ಮತ್ತೊಂದೆಡೆ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ದ್ವೇಷವನ್ನು ಬಿತ್ತುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಕ್ಷುಣ್ಣ ಕಾರಣಗಳನ್ನು ಮುಂದೆಮಾಡಿ ಗಲಭೆ, ದೊಂಬಿಗಳನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ಶಾಂತಿ- ಸುವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಕದಡುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಮತ್ತೊಂದು ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ಸೌಹಾರ್ದತೆ, ಸಮರಸ್ಯದಿಂದ ನಡೆಸಬೇಕಾದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಕೇವಲ ಅವರ ಅಧಿಕಾರದ ಲಾಲಸೆಗಾಗಿ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಭವನಗಳನ್ನು ದುರುಪಯೋಗ ಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ದುಷ್ಪ್ರತನವೆಂದೇ ಹೇಳಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಜಾತಿ - ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳಲ್ಲೂ ಕಿತ್ತು ತಿನ್ನುವ ಬಡತನವಿದ್ದು, ತಮ್ಮ ಮಕ್ಕಳಿಗೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣವನ್ನೂ ತಲೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಒಂದು ಸೂರನ್ನೂ ನೀಡಲು ಶಕ್ತರಲ್ಲದ ಜನರಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇವರ ಉನ್ನತಿಗಾಗಿ ಯಾವ ಜಾತಿ - ಸಮುದಾಯವನ್ನು ಮುಂದೆ ತಂದು ಬೀದಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಬಡಿದಾಡುವ ಜನರು ಮಾತನ್ನೇ ಆಡುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಅವರ ಏಳಿಗೆಗಾಗಿ ಯಾವ ರೀತಿಯ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನೂ ಹಮ್ಮಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಅದರ ಕುರಿ ಚರ್ಚಿಸುವುದೂ ಇಲ್ಲ ಎಂಬುದು ಖೇದಕರ. ಇಂತಹ ವಿಷಯಗಳು ಚರ್ಚೆಗೆ ಒಳಪಡಬಾರದು ಎಂಬುದೇ ಈ ಜಾತಿ - ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಉದ್ದೇಶವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಜಾತಿ - ಸಮುದಾಯ ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಒಳನೋಟ:

ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಗುರುತುಗಳು, ಆಸಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಶಕ್ತಿಯ ಚಲನಶೀಲತೆಯನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಗುಂಪುಗಳ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಒತ್ತಿಹೇಳುವ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ತಂತ್ರಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಚಳುವಳಿಗಳನ್ನು ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ವಿಧಾನವು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಅಂಚಿನಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಅಥವಾ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕವಾಗಿ ತುಳಿತಕ್ಕೊಳಗಾದ ಗುಂಪುಗಳನ್ನು ಅವರ ಸಾಮೂಹಿಕ ಗುರುತಿನ ಸುತ್ತಲೂ ಸಂಘಟಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳು, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳ ಸಮಾನ ಹಂಚಿಕೆಗೆ ಒತ್ತಾಯಿಸಲು ಅವರನ್ನು ಸಜ್ಜುಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ವಿಷಯಗಳನ್ನು ಕೆಳಕಂಡ ಅಂಶಗಳ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ವಿವರಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.

ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯ ರಾಜಕಾರಣವನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು:

ಜಾತಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ: ಈ ಪದವು ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಏಷ್ಯಾದ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತವಾಗಿದೆ, ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳ ಪ್ರವೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿಯು ಮಹತ್ವದ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಜಾತಿ-ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ತಮ್ಮ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಗಳಿಗಾಗಿ ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸಲು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿ ಗುಂಪುಗಳ (ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗೆ ದಲಿತರು, ಒಬಿಸಿಗಳು ಅಥವಾ ಮೇಲ್ಜಾತಿಗಳು) ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಜ್ಜುಗೊಳಿಸುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುತ್ತದೆ.

ದಲಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯ: ಕೆಳ-ಜಾತಿ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ, ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಜಾತಿ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಅಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕವಾಗಿ ತುಳಿತಕ್ಕೊಳಗಾದವರು ಸಂಘಟಿತರಾಗಲು ನೆರವುನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ.

ಇತರ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ವರ್ಗಗಳ ರಾಜಕೀಯ: ಮೇಲ್ಜಾತಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ದಲಿತರ ನಡುವೆ ಬೀಳುವ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ರೋಢೀಕರಣವನ್ನು ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸುತ್ತದೆ, ಆಗಾಗ್ಗೆ ಸಕಾರಾತ್ಮಕ ಕ್ರಮ ಮತ್ತು ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಅವಕಾಶಗಳಿಗಾಗಿ ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಮೇಲ್ಜಾತಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ: ಕೆಲವು ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳಲ್ಲಿ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳ ಮುಖಾಂತರ ತಮ್ಮ ಸವಲತ್ತುಗಳನ್ನು ರಕ್ಷಿಸಲು ಕೆಲವು ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳಲ್ಲಿ, ಮೇಲ್ಜಾತಿ ಗುಂಪುಗಳು ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ ಸಂಘಟಿಸುತ್ತವೆ.

ಸಮುದಾಯ-ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯ: ಇದು ಜನಾಂಗೀಯ, ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ, ಅಥವಾ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಗುರುತಿನ ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯವನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದು.

ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗೆ:

1. ಜನಾಂಗೀಯ ಅಥವಾ ಭಾಷಿಕ ಸಮುದಾಯ ರಾಜಕೀಯ: ಅನೇಕ ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ, ಜನಾಂಗೀಯ ಅಥವಾ ಭಾಷಾ ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರು ತಮ್ಮ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸಲು, ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವಗಳನ್ನು ಸಂರಕ್ಷಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ವಾಯತ್ತ ಅಥವಾ ಸ್ವ-ನಿರ್ಣಯಕ್ಕೆ (ಉದಾ., ಸ್ವೀನ್‌ನಲ್ಲಿ ಬಾಸ್ಕ್ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಅಥವಾ ತಮಿಳು ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ) ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ ಸಂಘಟಿತರಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಶ್ರೀಲಂಕಾ.

2. ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಸಮುದಾಯ ರಾಜಕೀಯ: ಧರ್ಮವು ಪ್ರಬಲವಾದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸುವ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ, ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ನಂಬಿಕೆಯ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳಿಗಾಗಿ (ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗೆ, ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಿಂದೂ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯತೆ, ಅಥವಾ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ ಗುರುತಿನ ರಾಜಕೀಯ) ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸಲು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಗುರುತುಗಳ ಸುತ್ತಲೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಗುಂಪುಗಳು ರಚಿಸಬಹುದು.

ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯ-ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಲಕ್ಷಣಗಳು:

1. ಐಡೆಂಟಿಟಿ-ಆಧಾರಿತ ಸಜ್ಜುಗೊಳಿಸುವಿಕೆ : ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಈ ರೂಪಗಳು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಗುಂಪಿನ ಸಾಮೂಹಿಕ ಗುರುತನ್ನು ಆಧರಿಸಿವೆ-ಅದು ಜಾತಿ, ಧರ್ಮ, ಜನಾಂಗೀಯತೆ ಅಥವಾ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯತೆ. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ರಮ ಮತ್ತು ನೀತಿಗಳು ಗುಂಪನ್ನು ಉನ್ನತೀಕರಿಸಲು ಅಥವಾ ಅದರ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ರಕ್ಷಿಸಲು ವಿನ್ಯಾಸಗೊಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.
2. ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮತೆಗಾಗಿ ಹಂಬಲ: ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ವಿಷಯವೆಂದರೆ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಅನ್ಯಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ಅಂಚಿನಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳ ನ್ಯಾಯಯುತ ಪಾಲನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯುವುದನ್ನು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು. ಇದು ದೃಢವಾದ ಕ್ರಮ, ಭೂ ಪುನರ್ವಿತರಣೆ ಅಥವಾ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ತಾರತಮ್ಯವನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡಲು ವಿನ್ಯಾಸಗೊಳಿಸಿದ ನೀತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರಬಹುದು.
3. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯ: ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ, ಈ ಚಳುವಳಿಗಳು ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗಗಳು, ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು ಅಥವಾ ಇತರ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಗುಂಪುಗಳಿಗೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯವನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಇದು ಅವರ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಕಾಳಜಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅಗತ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.
4. ಸಮುದಾಯ ನಿರ್ಮಾಣ ಮತ್ತು ಒಗ್ಗಟ್ಟು: ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಸದಸ್ಯರ ನಡುವೆ ಒಗ್ಗಟ್ಟನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸುವುದು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಗಳು ಸಾಮೂಹಿಕ ಬಲವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದುವುದನ್ನು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದು ಪ್ರತಿಭಟನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸಂಘಟಿಸುವುದು, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳನ್ನು ರಚಿಸುವುದು ಅಥವಾ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳನ್ನು ರಚಿಸುವುದು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರಬಹುದು.

ಸವಾಲುಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಟೀಕೆಗಳು:

ವಿಭಜನೆ : ಜಾತಿ ಅಥವಾ ಸಮುದಾಯ ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಒಂದು ಟೀಕೆ ಎಂದರೆ ಅದು ಸಮಾಜವನ್ನು ಭಿದ್ರಗೊಳಿಸಬಹುದು ಮತ್ತು ವಿಭಜನೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಬಹುದು. ಗುಂಪಿನ ಗುರುತಿನ ಮೇಲೆ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ, ಈ ಚಳುವಳಿಗಳು ಕೆಲವೊಮ್ಮೆ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಏಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವ ಬದಲು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಬಿರುಕುಗಳನ್ನು ಬಲಪಡಿಸಬಹುದು.

ಪೋಷಕ ರಾಜಕಾರಣ: ಜಾತಿ ಅಥವಾ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಮೇಲೆ ತಮ್ಮ ಮನವಿಯನ್ನು ಆಧರಿಸಿದ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ತಮ್ಮ ಮತದಾರರಿಗೆ ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹವನ್ನು (ಅಂದರೆ, ಒಲವು ಅಥವಾ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳು) ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ, ಇದು ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಬಹುದು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ದುರ್ಬಲಗೊಳಿಸಬಹುದು.

ಬಹಿಷ್ಕಾರದ ಅಭ್ಯಾಸಗಳು: ಈ ಚಳುವಳಿಗಳು ಅಂಚಿನಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಗುಂಪುಗಳನ್ನು ಸಬಲೀಕರಣಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಗುರಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದರೂ, ಅವು ಕೆಲವೊಮ್ಮೆ ಇತರರನ್ನು ಅಂಚಿನಲ್ಲಿಡಬಹುದು. ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗೆ, ಜಾತಿ-ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ಒಂದು ಗುಂಪಿನ ಮೇಲೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಗಮನಹರಿಸಬಹುದು, ಅದು ಇತರರನ್ನು ಕಡೆಗಣಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಅಥವಾ ದೂರವಿಡುತ್ತದೆ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಸಂಘರ್ಷದ ಹೊಸ ರೂಪಗಳನ್ನು ಸಂಭಾವ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಸುಸ್ಥಿರತೆ: ತಕ್ಷಣದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಒಮ್ಮೆ ಪರಿಹರಿಸಿದ ನಂತರ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯ-ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ಯಾವಾಗಲೂ ಗುರುತು-ಆಧಾರಿತ ಚೌಕಟ್ಟನ್ನು ಮೀರದಿರಬಹುದು, ಇದು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಭಾವ್ಯ ನಿಶ್ಚಲತೆ ಅಥವಾ ಹಿನ್ನಡೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯ-ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದ ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗಳು:

ಭಾರತ : ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭೂದೃಶ್ಯವು ಜಾತಿ ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಿಂದ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಪ್ರಭಾವಿತವಾಗಿದೆ. ಮಾಯಾವತಿ ನೇತೃತ್ವದ ಬಹುಜನ ಸಮಾಜ ಪಕ್ಷ (ಃಖಕ) ನಂತರ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ದಲಿತ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಸುತ್ತವೆ, ಆದರೆ ಭಾರತೀಯ

ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಮತ್ತು ಇತರ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಕೆಲವೊಮ್ಮೆ ಔಪಚಾರಿಕ ಗುಂಪುಗಳನ್ನು ಸಜ್ಜುಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಉದ್ಯೋಗಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿ-ಆಧಾರಿತ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಗಳಂತಹ ದೃಢವಾದ ಕ್ರಿಯೆಯ ನೀತಿಗಳು ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿನ ಜಾತಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಸುತ್ತಲಿನ ಚರ್ಚೆಗೆ ಕೇಂದ್ರವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಶ್ರೀಲಂಕಾ : ತಮಿಳು ಜನಾಂಗೀಯ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ಶ್ರೀಲಂಕಾದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಶಕ್ತಿಯಾಗಿದೆ, ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ತಮಿಳು ಈಳಮ್‌ಗಾಗಿ ತಮಿಳು ಹುಲಿಗಳ ಚಳುವಳಿಯೊಂದಿಗೆ, ಸಿಂಹಳೀಯ ಬಹುಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಿಂದ ಜನಾಂಗೀಯ ಉದ್ವಿಗ್ನತೆಗಳು ಉಲ್ಬಣಗೊಂಡಿವೆ.

ಯುನೈಟೆಡ್ ಸ್ಟೇಟ್ಸ್ ಆಫ್ ಅಮೇರಿಕ: ಜಾತಿಯನ್ನು ಆಧರಿಸಿಲ್ಲದಿದ್ದರೂ, ಅಮೇರಿಕಾದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮುದಾಯ-ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಜನಾಂಗೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಜನಾಂಗೀಯ ಗುರುತುಗಳ ಸುತ್ತ ಸುತ್ತುತ್ತದೆ. ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗೆ, ಆಫ್ರಿಕನ್ ಅಮೇರಿಕನ್ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕವಾಗಿ ವರ್ಣಭೇದ ನೀತಿಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಿಸಿದೆ.

ಟರ್ಕಿ ಮತ್ತು ಕುರ್ದಿಗಳು : ಟರ್ಕಿ, ಇರಾಕ್ ಮತ್ತು ಸಿರಿಯಾದಲ್ಲಿನ ಕುರ್ದಿಶ್ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಚಳುವಳಿಗಳು ಸಮುದಾಯ-ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಒಂದು ರೂಪವಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಸ್ವಯಂ-ನಿರ್ಣಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಗೆ ಜನಾಂಗೀಯ ಗುರುತು ಕೇಂದ್ರವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಜಾತಿ/ಸಮುದಾಯ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ನಾಯಕತ್ವದ ಪಾತ್ರ :

ಈ ಆಂದೋಲನಗಳ ಯಶಸ್ಸಿಗೆ ಬಲಿಷ್ಠ ನಾಯಕತ್ವವು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಅತ್ಯಗತ್ಯ. ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಕುಂದುಕೊರತೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಮುನ್ನೆಲೆಗೆ ತರುವ ಮತ್ತು ಸದಸ್ಯರನ್ನು ಒಗ್ಗೂಡಿಸುವ ವರ್ಚಸ್ವಿ ನಾಯಕರು ಈ ಚಳುವಳಿಗಳ ಮುಂಚೂಣಿಯಲ್ಲಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ.

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಡಾ|| ಬಿ ಆರ್ ಅಂಬೇಡ್ಕರ್ ಅವರು ದಲಿತ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯವನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸಿದರು ಮತ್ತು ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಕರಡು ರಚನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸಿದರು.

ಮಾಯಾವತಿ, ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ದಲಿತ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ನೆಲ್ಸನ್ ಮಂಡೇಲಾ ಮತ್ತು ಮಾರ್ಟಿನ್ ಲೂಥರ್ ಕಿಂಗ್ ಜೂ. ಕೆಲವು ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗಳಷ್ಟೆ.

ಜಾತಿ - ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಿಂದ ಉಂಟಾಗುವ ಅಪಾಯವೇನು?

ಈ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಯು ಬಹಳ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾದುದು. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಿರುವ ಜಾತಿ - ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಿಂದ ಉಂಟಾಗುವ ನಷ್ಟವೆಂದರೆ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳ ಮಾರಣಹೋಮವೇ ಆಗಿದೆ. ಫ್ರೆಂಚ್ ಕ್ರಾಂತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಒಡಮೂಡಿದ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳಾದ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ, ಸಮಾನತೆ, ಭಾಷ್ಯ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಗಳು ಇಂದಿನ ಜಾತಿ - ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ದಾಳಿಗೆ ಸಿಲುಕಿ ನಲುಗಿ ಹೋಗಿವೆ. ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನವು ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ, ಸಮಾನತೆ, ಭಾಷ್ಯ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾಗ್ಯೂ ಅವುಗಳ ಪೂರ್ಣ ಪ್ರಮಾಣದ ಜಾರಿ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂಬುದು ಕಟು ಸತ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 19 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಆರು ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದ್ದು ಅವುಗಳು ಈ ಮುಂದಿನಂತಿವೆ.

- ವಾಕ್ ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ
- ಶಾಂತಿಯಿಂದ ಮತ್ತು ನಿರಾಯುಧರಾಗಿ ಸಭೆ ಸೇರುವ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ
- ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳನ್ನಯ ಅಥವಾ ಸಂಘಗಳನ್ನು ತಚ್ಛಿಸುವ ಅಥವಾ ಸಹಕಾರಿ ಸಂಘಗಳನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ
- ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಬಾಧಿತವಾಗಿ ಸರ್ವತ್ರ ಸಂಚಾರ ಸಂಚಾರ ಮಾಡುವ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ
- ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದ ಯಾವುದೇ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸಮಾಡುವ ಮತ್ತು ನೆಲೆಸುವ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ
- ಯಾವುದೇ ವೃತ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವ ಅಥವಾ ಕಸುಬನ್ನು, ವ್ಯಾಪಾರವನ್ನು ಅಥವಾ ವ್ಯವಹಾರವನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ

ವಾಕ್ ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯದ ಮೇಲೆ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯ ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ದಾಳಿ:

ವಾಕ್ ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯವು ಪ್ರಜಾತಂತ್ರದ ಬಹು ಮುಖ್ಯವಾದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಬರ್ಚಿಂಡ್ ರಸೆಲ್ ರವರ ವಾಣಿಯು ಅದರ ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಅದನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬೇಕಾದ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಅದೊಂದರೆ "ನಾನು ನಿಮ್ಮ ವಾದವನ್ನು ಒಪ್ಪದೇ ಇರಬಹುದು. ಆದರೆ ನಿಮ್ಮ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯವನ್ನು ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸಲು ನಿಮಗಿರುವ ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯವನ್ನು ರಕ್ಷಿಸಲು ನನ್ನ ಪ್ರಾಣವನ್ನೇ ನೀಡಲು ಸಿದ್ಧನಿದ್ದೇನೆ." ಈ ಮಾತುಗಳಲ್ಲಿರುವ ನಿಜವಾದ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವನೆ ಇಂದಿನ ದಿನಮಾನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಇಲ್ಲದಿರುವುದು ದುಃಖಕರವಾದುದು.

ದೇಶದಲ್ಲೆಡೆ ಜಾತಿ - ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಧ್ವನಿ ಎತ್ತುವ ಜನರನ್ನು ಗುರಿಯಾಗಿರಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ದಾಳಿ, ಲೇವಡಿ, ಮಾನಹಾನಿ ಉಂಟುಮಾಡುವಂತಹ ಮಾತುಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ದಾಳಿ ಪ್ರಾರಂಭವಾಗಿ ಈ ಯಾವ ದಾಳಿಗೂ ಜಗ್ಗದೇ ಇದ್ದಾಗ ಅಂತಹ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳ ಪ್ರಾಣಕ್ಕೆ ಅಪಾಯ ಒಡ್ಡುವ, ಹತ್ಯೆಗೈಯುವ ಪ್ರವೃತ್ತಿಗಳು ಉಲ್ಬಣಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಜಾತಿ - ಸಮುದಾಯ ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದ ದುಷ್ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಯ ಪರಿಣಾಮವಾಗಿ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಭಾಗ ಮೂರರಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಧಿ 19 ರಲ್ಲಿನ ವಾಕ್ ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯದ ರಕ್ಷಣೆ ಮರೀಚಿಕೆಯಾಗಿದೆ.

ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 21 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಧಾನ ಮಾಡಲಾಗಿರುವ ಜೀವಿಸುವ ಹಕ್ಕು ಹಾಗೂ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಸವಾಲು:

ಜಾತಿ - ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ತಾರತಮ್ಯದ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿ ಇತ್ತೀಚೆಗೆ ಈ ತಾರತಮ್ಯವನ್ನು ಹೋಗಲಾಡಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ಸರ್ವೋಚ್ಚ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಲಯವು ಹಲವು ಪ್ರಕರಣಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಪಟ್ಟಿರುವುದು ಸ್ವಲ್ಪ ಮಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಆಶಾದಾಯಕವಾದುದಾಗಿದೆ. ತಮ್ಮ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವಿರೋಧಿಗಳನ್ನು ಭಯ-ಭೀತರನ್ನಾಗಿಸಲು ಹಾಗೂ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಭಾವನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕೆರಳಿಸಲು ಈ ಭಯವನ್ನು ಉಂಟುಮಾಡುವ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯು ಇತ್ತೀಚಿನ ಜಾತಿ - ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಆವಿಷ್ಕರಿಸಿದ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ನೀಚ ಹಾಗೂ ದುಷ್ಪರಿಧಾನವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಭಯವನ್ನು ಉಂಟುಮಾಡುವ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯು ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಭಾಗ ಮೂರರಲ್ಲಿನ ವಿಧಿ 21 ರ ಆಶಯಕ್ಕೆ ತದ್ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾದ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಯಾಗಿದೆ.

ಕೇವಲ ಸಂಶಯದ ಕಾರಣದಿಂದಾಗಿ ಖಾಸಗಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳ ಮನೆಯನ್ನು ಶೋಧಿಸಲು ಮುಂದಾಗುವ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ವಿಧಿ 21 ರಲ್ಲಿನ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯ ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕತೆಯ ಹಕ್ಕನ್ನು ಉಲ್ಲಂಘಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಇಂದಿನ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಸಂಗತಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಖಾಸಗಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳಿಗೆ, ಮತ್ತೊಬ್ಬ ಖಾಸಗಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯ ಖಾಸಗಿತನವನ್ನು ಭಂಗಪಡಿಸುವ ಧೈರ್ಯ ಹಾಗೂ ಭಂಡತನವನ್ನು ದಯಪಾಲಿಸಿದ್ದು ಬೇರಾವ ರಾಜಕೀಯವೂ ಅಲ್ಲ, ಬದಲಿಗೆ ಜಾತಿ - ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯವೇ ಆಗಿದೆ. ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯ ಆಧಾರಿತವಾದ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ದಾಳಿಯು ನೇರವಾಗಿ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ದತ್ತವಾದ ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಸುಳ್ಳಲ್ಲ.

ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತವಾದ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಕರಾಳ ಮನೋಭಾವನೆಯನ್ನು ನಿವಾರಿಸಲು ಇರುವ ಪರಿಹಾರೋಪಾಯಗಳು:

ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಕರಾಳ ಮನೋಭಾವನೆಯನ್ನು ನಿವಾರಿಸಲು ಇರುವ ಪರಿಹಾರಗಳೆಂದರೆ,

- 1) ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಜಾತಿಗಳ ಅಥವಾ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಹೆಸರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ನೀಡುವ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಗಿತಗೊಳಿಸಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಸ್ಥಿತಿ-ಗತಿಯನ್ನು ಆಧರಿಸಿ ಒದಗಿಸಬೇಕು.
- 2) ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿ ಅಥವಾ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಹೆಸರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳನ್ನು ನೋಂದಾಯಿಸುವುದು, ಹಾಗೂ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ವಾತಾವರಣವನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸಲು ಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.
- 3) ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಆಧಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ತಾರತಮ್ಯವನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿ ಮಾಡುವ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸಾಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ ಉಪಬಂಧಗಳನ್ನೂ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಸಿ ಪರಿಷ್ಕರಿಸಿ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಹಾಗೂ ಕಾನೂನಿನ ಮುಂದೆ ಸಮಾನತೆ ತತ್ವವನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಶ್ರಮಿಸಬೇಕು.
- 4) ಜಾತಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಬಳಸುವ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಚಿಹ್ನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕವಾಗಿ ಬಳಕೆ ಮಾಡುವುದನ್ನು ನಿಷೇಧಿಸಬೇಕು.
- 5) ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಕಛೇರಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ಇಲಾಖೆ, ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ದೇವರ ಪೂಜೆ, ಆರಾಧನೆ, ಆಚರಣೆಗಳಂತಹ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ, ಆಧ್ಯಾತ್ಮಿಕ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಿಷೇಧಿಸಬೇಕು ಮತ್ತು ತನ್ಮೂಲಕ ತಾನೊಬ್ಬ ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದ ಪ್ರಜೆ ಎಂಬ ಹೆಮ್ಮೆಯ ಮನೋಭಾವನೆಯನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸಬೇಕು.
- 6) ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಸ್ಥಿತಿ-ಗತಿಗಳೇ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಏಕಮಾತ್ರ ಮಾನದಂಡವನ್ನಾಗಿ ಘೋಷಿಸಬೇಕು.
- 7) ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಚಾರ ಮಾಡಲು ಅಗತ್ಯ ಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.
- 8) ಭ್ರಾತೃತ್ವ ಮನೋಭಾವನೆಯನ್ನು ವೃದ್ಧಿಸಲು ಅಗತ್ಯ ಪ್ರಚಾರ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.

ಮೇಲ್ಕಂಡ ಹಲವು ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸಮಾಜದ ಹಿತಚಿಂತಕರ ಸಲಹೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಕಾಲಕಾಲಕ್ಕೆ ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾ ಜಾತಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಪ್ರಭಾವವನ್ನು ಇಲ್ಲವಾಗಿಸಿ ವಿಶ್ವಮಾನವ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರಚುರಪಡಿಸಬೇಕು.

ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಹೆಸರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ನೀಡುವ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಇಲ್ಲವಾಗಿಸುವುದರಿಂದ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯನ್ನು ತೆಗೆಯಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬ ಆತಂಕದ ಲಾಭ ಪಡೆಯಲು ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯಕ್ಕೆ ಅವಕಾಶವಿಲ್ಲದಂತೆ, ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿನ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಬಡ ವರ್ಗದ ಜನರಿಗೂ ಅವರವರ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಗತಿಗೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿ ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ರಕ್ಷಣೆ ನೀಡುವುದು ಎಂಬ ಭರವಸೆಯನ್ನು ಹಾಗೂ ಬಲವಾದ ನಂಬಿಕೆಯನ್ನೂ ಉಂಟುಮಾಡಬೇಕು. ಆಗಮಾತ್ರ ಜಾತಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಸಮುದಾಯಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯವನ್ನು ಸೋಲಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯ.

ಹಿಂದಿನಿಂದಲೂ ಸಮಾಜವು ಬದಲಾಗಿದೆ, ಈಗಿನ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಯಲ್ಲೂ ಸಮಾಜವು ಬದಲಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ, ಭವಿಷ್ಯದ ದಿನಮಾನಗಳಲ್ಲೂ ಸಮಾಜವು ಬದಲಾಗುತ್ತಿರುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬ ಸತ್ಯವನ್ನು ಎಲ್ಲೆಡೆ ಹರಡಬೇಕು.

ತೀರ್ಮಾನ:

ಒಂದೆಡೆ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯ-ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥಿತ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಯನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು, ಒಗ್ಗಟ್ಟನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕವಾಗಿ ಅಂಚಿನಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಗುಂಪುಗಳ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳಿಗಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಬಲ ಸಾಧನಗಳಾಗಿವೆ. ಆದಾಗ್ಯೂ, ಅವರು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಏಕತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಒಗ್ಗಟ್ಟಿನ ವಿಷಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತಪಡಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಐಡೆಂಟಿಟಿ-ಆಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ತಪ್ಪುಗಳನ್ನು ಸರಿಪಡಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ತುಳಿತಕ್ಕೊಳಗಾದ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳಿಗೆ ನ್ಯಾಯವನ್ನು ತರಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡಬಹುದಾದರೂ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ವಿಭಜನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಬಲಪಡಿಸುವುದನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಹೊರಗಿಡುವಿಕೆಯ ಹೊಸ ರೂಪಗಳನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸುವುದನ್ನು ತಪ್ಪಿಸಲು ಎಚ್ಚರಿಕೆಯ ನಿರ್ವಹಣೆಯ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿದೆ. ಅಂತಿಮವಾಗಿ, ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಗುಂಪುಗಳು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಅಧಿಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಸಮಾನ ಪ್ರವೇಶವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಅಂತರ್ಗತ ಸಮಾಜವನ್ನು ರಚಿಸುವುದು ಗುರಿಯಾಗಿದೆ.

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12. ಮೆರುಗು ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು-5600073.
13. ಅಂತರ್ಜಾಲ
14. ದಿನಪತ್ರಿಕೆಗಳು, ವೃತ್ತ ಪತ್ರಿಕೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳು ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ

ಪಂಚಾಯತ್‌ರಾಜ್ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣದ ಒಂದು ಅಧ್ಯಯನ

ಡಾ. ಪ್ರವೀಣ್‌ಕುಮಾರ್ ಓ

ಸಹಾಯಕ ಪ್ರಾಧ್ಯಾಪಕರು

ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ವಿಭಾಗ

ಮಾ.ಸ.ಬ. ಕಲಾ ಮತ್ತು ವಾಣಿಜ್ಯ ಕಾಲೇಜು, ದಾವಣಗೆರೆ

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ಸಾರಲೇಖ

ಭಾರತದ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣದ ಕುರಿತ ವಿಚಾರವು ಬಹುಹಿಂದಿನಿಂದಲೂ ಬೆಳೆದು ಬಂದ ಒಂದು ಹೋರಾಟದ ವಸ್ತು ವಿಷಯವಾಗಿದೆ. 1980 ರ ದಶಕ ಮಧ್ಯಭಾಗದಿಂದಾಗಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ತಮ್ಮ ದಬ್ಬಾಳಿಕೆಯ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಗತಿಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿವಿಧ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಚಳವಳಿಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಬೆಳಕು ಚೆಲ್ಲುತ್ತಿದ್ದರಿಂದ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯು ಬೆಳಕಿಗೆ ಬಂದಿದೆ. ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ, ಕಾರ್ಪೊರೇಟ್ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ, ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಯ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಪಾಲ್ಗೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ಕಂಡು ಬಂದಿದೆ. ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸುಧಾರಣೆ ತರುವ ಉದ್ದೇಶವು ಅವರಿಗೆ ಸಶಕ್ತವಾದ ಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಯಶಸ್ವಿಯಾಗಬಹುದು. ಎಲ್ಲ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣವು ಅವರ ಪ್ರಗತಿಗೆ ಮತ್ತು ಲಿಂಗ ಸಮಾನ ಸಮಾಜದ ಅಡಿಪಾಯಕ್ಕೆ ಬಹುಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದು ಸಮಾನತೆಯ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಮತ್ತು ಶಾಂತಿಯ ಗುರಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಕೇಂದ್ರವಾಗಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಸಂಶೋಧನಾ ಲೇಖನವು ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಪಾಲ್ಗೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಪಾತ್ರ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿಗಳನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸುವ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನವನ್ನು ಈ ಲೇಖನದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾಡಲಾಗಿದೆ.

ಮುಖ್ಯ ಪದಗಳು:-ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಹಿನಿ, ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಸಭೆ, ವಿಶೇಷ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು, ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಯೋಜನೆ, ಭಾಗ್ಯಲಕ್ಷ್ಮಿ ಯೋಜನೆ, ವಿಧವಾ ವೇತನ.

ಪೀಠಿಕೆ

“ನಾನು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಸಂಘಟನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅತಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ನಂಬಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅವರು ಒಪ್ಪಿದ್ದರೆ ಸಮಾಜದ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಗತಿಯನ್ನು ಬದಲಾಯಿಸಬಲ್ಲರು ಎನ್ನುವುದು ನನ್ನಿಗೆ ಗೊತ್ತಿದೆ. ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಪಿಡುಗುಗಳ ನಿವಾರಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅವರು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಸೇವೆ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂದು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಹೇಳಿದ ಡಾ.ಬಿ.ಆರ್.ಅಂಬೇಡ್ಕರವರ ಕೊಡುಗೆ ಬಹಳ ಅಪಾರವಾದದ್ದು.

ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ ಇಂದು ನಿನ್ನೆಯದಲ್ಲ, ಗಂಡು ಹೆಣ್ಣಿನ ನಡುವೆ ತಾರತಮ್ಯ ನೀತಿ ಎಂದಿನಿಂದ ಶುರುವಾಯಿತೋ ಅಂದಿನಿಂದಲೂ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಸಶಕ್ತೀಕರಣದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ ಬೆಳೆಯುತ್ತಲೇ ಬಂದಿದೆ. ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರ ಅಸಾಧಾರಣ ಬುದ್ಧಿಮತ್ತೆ ಸಾಧನಗಳಿಗೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗಳು ವೇದಗಳ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಸಿಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಜೀವನದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಹಂತಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಯಾವುದೇ ಸಮಾಜದ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಗೆ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣವು ಅಗತ್ಯ ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಯಾಗಿದೆ ಜನಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯ ಅರ್ಧದಷ್ಟು ಭಾಗವನ್ನು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದರೂ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸ್ಥಾನಮಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಸಮಾನವೆಂದು ಅವರು ನಿಗ್ರಹಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಸ್ವಾಭಿಮಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ವಾಯತ್ತತೆಗೆ ಹೋರಾಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣ

ಮಹಿಳೆಯರನ್ನು ಇನ್ನು ಒಂದು ಭೋಗದ ವಸ್ತುವಾಗಿ ಉಪಯೋಗಿಸಿ ಎಸೆಯಲಾಗುತ್ತಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಸಮಾಜದ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಹಿನಿಯಿಂದ ಅವಳನ್ನು ದೂರ ಇಟ್ಟು ಕಡೆಗಣಿಸಲಾಗುತ್ತಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಇನ್ನು ಅಶಕ್ತರಿರುವುದರಿಂದಲೇ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣ ಎಂಬ ವಿಷಯವು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಮಹತ್ವ ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅವರು ಸಶಕ್ತರಾಗುವ ತನಕ ಮುಂದುವರಿಯುತ್ತಲೇ ಇರುತ್ತದೆ. ಪುರುಷ ಪ್ರಧಾನವಾದ ಈ ಸಮಾಜವು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೆ ಯಾವಾಗಲೂ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ವಯಂ ಆಡಳಿತವನ್ನು ನಿರಾಕರಿಸುತ್ತಾ ಬಂದಿದೆ. ಈ ಲಿಂಗ ತಾರತಮ್ಯವು ಮಾನವೀಯ ಮುಖವನ್ನು ವಿಕಾರಗೊಳಿಸಿದೆ. ಈ ತಾರತಮ್ಯವು ಹೆಣ್ಣು ಮಗುವಿನ ಜನನಕ್ಕೆ ಮುಂಚೆಯೇ ಪ್ರಾರಂಭವಾಗಿ ಅದು ಅವಳ ಹೆಣ್ಣುತನದ ಜೀವನಗಂಟಾಗಿ ಉಳಿದು ಬಿಡುತ್ತದೆ ಜಗತ್ತಿನ ಅತಿದೊಡ್ಡ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೆ ಉನ್ನತ ಸ್ಥಾನ ಕೊಟ್ಟಿದ್ದೆವೆ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಒಟ್ಟು ಜನಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯ ಶೇ50 ರಷ್ಟನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ ಆದರೂ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರನ್ನು ದ್ವಿತೀಯ ದರ್ಜೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ನೋಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ

ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣವೆಂದರೆ ಸ್ವಗೌರವ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠೆಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು, ಆರ್ಥಿಕವಾಗಿ ಸ್ವಾವಲಂಬನೆ ಯಾಗುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ವಂತಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದುವುದು ಎಂದರ್ಥ. ಇತಿಹಾಸವನ್ನು ಅವಲೋಕಿಸಿದಾಗ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯಕ್ಕಾಗಿ

ಶ್ರಮಿಸಿದ ಅನೇಕ ಮಹನೀಯರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ತಿಳಿದು ಬರುತ್ತದೆ ಅವರಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾದವರು,ಬುದ್ಧ, ಬಸವಣ್ಣ, ರಾಜರಾಮಮೋಹನರಾಯ, ಈಶ್ವರಚಂದ್ರವಿದ್ಯಾಸಾಗರ, ಸ್ವಾಮಿವಿವೇಕನಂದ. ಮಹಾತ್ಮಗಾಂಧಿ, ನೆಹರು ಮುಂತಾದವರು ಇವರಲ್ಲದೇ ಬ್ರಿಟಿಷ್ ಸರಕಾರವು ಕೂಡ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಸಶಸ್ತ್ರಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಕೆಲವೊಂದು ಕಾನೂನುಗಳನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತಂದರು. ಆದರೆ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರನ್ನು ಸಬಲೀಕರಣಗೊಳಿಸಬೇಕೆಂಬ ಇಚ್ಛೆ ಹೊಂದಿದ ಜನರಿಂದ ಮಾತ್ರ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣ ಮಾಡಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಸ್ವಂತ ತಾವೇ ಮುಂದೆ ಬಂದು ಯಾವುದೇ ಜಾತಿದರ್ಮ ಎಂದು ಭೇದ ಮಾಡದೇ ತಮ್ಮ ಸಶಸ್ತ್ರಕರಣದ ಕಡೆಗೆ ಒಗ್ಗಟ್ಟಾಗಿ ಮುಂದೆ ಸಾಗಬೇಕು. ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಈಗಾಗಲೇ ಮಹತ್ವದ ಸಾಧನೆ ಮಾಡಿದ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಂದ ಪ್ರಭಾವಿತರಾಗಿ ಅವರ ಮಾರ್ಗವನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸಬೇಕು ಉದಾ-ಇಂದಿರಾಗಾಂಧಿ, ವಿಜಯಲಕ್ಷ್ಮೀ ಪಂಡಿತ, ಮದರತೇರೆಸಾ, ಸರೋಜಿನಿನಾಯ್ಡು, ಸುಚೇತಾಕೃಪಲಾನಿ, ಕಿರಣಬೇಡಿ ಮುಂತಾದವರು

ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪುರುಷರ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಕಮ್ಮಿ ಸರಿಸಮಾನವಾಗಿ ಮಹಿಳಾಬಾಹುಳ್ಯವಿದ್ದರೂ ಸಮಾಜದ ಹಲವು ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೆ ಸಮಾನತೆ ಗಗನಕುಸುಮವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ತಮಗೂ ಪುರುಷರಂತೆಯೇ ಸಮಾನಹಕ್ಕಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಭಾವಿಸುವಂತಾಗಬೇಕು ಈ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಬಾರಿಯು ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸಂಸದರ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯು ಹೆಚ್ಚಳ ಒಂದು ಸ್ವಾಗತಾರ್ಹ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆ ಎನ್ನಬಹುದು. 2014ರಲ್ಲಿ ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಿಂದ 21 ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿದ್ದು ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಒಬ್ಬರು ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಸದಸ್ಯರಾಗಿ ಆಯ್ಕೆಯಾಗಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. 2013ರ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ 175 ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿದ್ದು 6 ಜನ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆಗೆ ಆಯ್ಕೆಯಾಗಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. 543 ಸದಸ್ಯ ಬಲದ ಲೋಕಸಭೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯ ಶೇ33 ರ ಪ್ರಮಾಣ ಮುಟ್ಟಬೇಕೆಂದರೇ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಷ್ಟು ಟಿಕೆಟ್ ನೀಡುವ ಕುರಿತು ಚಿಂತನೆ ನಡೆಸಬೇಕಿರುವುದು ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯ. ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗುತ್ತಾ ಹೋದಂತೆ ಈ ವಲಯಕ್ಕೆ ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಬೇಕಾದ ಅವಕಾಶಗಳು ಹಮ್ಮಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾದ ಕಲ್ಯಾಣ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿಯೂ ಹಿಗ್ಗಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಈ ಕುರಿತಾದ ಸಮರ್ಥ ನೀಲನಕ್ಷೆ ವಿಸ್ತೃತಚರ್ಚೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನ ಆಗಬೇಕೆಂದರೇ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿ ಸಭೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ ಗಣನೀಯವಾಗಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಬೇಕು

ಭಾರತ ಮತ್ತು ಸುಭಾ (2002) ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣವನ್ನು “ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಯೋಜಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ನಿರ್ಣಯ ಮಾಡುವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆ, ಯೋಜನೆ, ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಮೌಲ್ಯ ಮಾಪನವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಭಾವಿಸುವ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯ ಎಂದು ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಿಸಿ ಇದು ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಹಂತಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾನ, ಸ್ಪರ್ಧೆ, ಪ್ರಚಾರ,ಪಕ್ಷದ ಸದಸ್ಯತ್ವ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯವನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುವ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಾಲ್ಗೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಸೂಚಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿ ಪ್ರಭಾವಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಮೂಲಕ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ

“ಭಾರತದ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಶಿಲ್ಪಿ ಡಾ. ಬಿ.ಆರ್. ಅಂಬೇಡ್ಕರರವರು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣದ ಕುರಿತು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗಾಗಿ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವರಿಸಿದ ಸವಲತ್ತುಗಳನ್ನು ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ 14ನೇ ವಿಧಿಯ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಪುರುಷ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಎಲ್ಲರಿಗೂ ಸಮಾನವಾದ ಕಾನೂನು ರಕ್ಷಣೆ ಕೊಡುತ್ತದೆ 15 ನೇ ವಿಧಿ ತಾರತಮ್ಯ ದೋರಣೆಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಬಂಧಿಸುತ್ತದೆ,16 ನೇ ವಿಧಿ ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ನೌಕರಿ ಹುದ್ದೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೆ ಸಮಾನತೆಹಕ್ಕು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ 330ನೇ ವಿಧಿ ಹಾಗೂ 332ನೇ ವಿಧಿಯ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡಗಳಿಗೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯನ್ನು ನೀಡುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ಅವಕಾಶವನ್ನು ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಿದೆ. 330ನೇ ವಿಧಿಯ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಲೋಕಸಭೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲವು ಸ್ಥಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡಗಳಿಗೆ ಮತ್ತು 332ನೇ ವಿಧಿಯ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ರಾಜ್ಯ ವಿಧಾನ ಸಭೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲವು ಸ್ಥಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡಗಳಿಗೆ ಮೀಸಲಿಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಹೀಗೆ ಮೀಸಲಿಟ್ಟ ಸ್ಥಾನಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡಗಳ ಜನಸಂಖ್ಯೆಗೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿರಬೇಕು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯಿಂದ ನೀತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಹಾಗೂ ಶಾಸನಗಳನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡಗಳ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ದೊರೆತಿದೆ. ಮೂಲತಃ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಜಾರಿಗೆ ಬಂದಾಗಿನಿಂದ 10 ವರ್ಷಗಳ ಕಾಲ(1960ರ ವರೆಗೆ) ಮಾತ್ರ ಈ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡಲಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಇದನ್ನು ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಹತ್ತು ವರ್ಷಗಳವರೆಗೆ ವಿಸ್ತರಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ 1990ರ 79ನೇ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಮೂಲಕ 60 ವರ್ಷಗಳಿಗೆ ಅಂದರೆ 2010ರವರೆಗೆ ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿಧಾನ ಸಭೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಥಾನ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ ವಿಸ್ತರಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. 2009ರಲ್ಲಿ 95ನೇ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಮೂಲಕ 70 ವರ್ಷಗಳಿಗೆ ಅಂದರೆ 2020ರ ವರೆಗೆ ವಿಸ್ತರಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.

ಪಂಚಾಯಿತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ: 1992ರಲ್ಲಿ 73ನೇ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಯನ್ನು ಮಾಡಲಾಯಿತು. ಈ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಯನ್ನು “ದಿ ಪಂಚಾಯಿತ್” ಎಂಬ ಶೀರ್ಷಿಕೆಯಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಮಾಡಲಾಯಿತು. ಈ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಯನ್ನು ಏಪ್ರಿಲ್ 20 1993ರಿಂದ ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಿತು. ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ 243ಡಿ ಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಥಾನಗಳ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ 1/3ರಷ್ಟು ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯನ್ನು ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಿತ್ತು.

ಅಧ್ಯಕ್ಷರುಗಳ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಗ್ರಾಮಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧ್ಯಕ್ಷರ ಹುದ್ದೆಯನ್ನು ರಾಜ್ಯ ವಿಧಾನ ಮಂಡಲವು ಕಾನೂನಿನ ಮೂಲಕ ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಿದ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪಂಗಡಗಳ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ಇತರೆ ವರ್ಗಗಳಿಗೆ ಮೀಸಲಿಡಲಾಗಿದೆ.

ಉದಾ- ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಜಿಲ್ಲಾ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್, ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕು ಪಂಚಾಯತ್, ಗ್ರಾಮಪಂಚಾಯತ್‌ಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಶೇ 15 ರಷ್ಟು ಹಾಗೂ ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡಗಳಿಗೆ ಶೇ. 3ರಷ್ಟು ಸ್ಥಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಮೀಸಲಿಡಲಾಗಿದೆ.

ಬಡ್ಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ : 1995ರಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾರಿಗೆ ಬಂದ 77 ನೇ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಹುದ್ದೆಗಳಿಗೆ ನೀಡಲಾಗುವ ಬಡ್ಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ ನೀಡಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡಿದೆ. ಬದಲಾದ ಆಧುನಿಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲೂ ಇಂದು ಪ್ರಬಲವಾಗಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ

ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಸರಕಾರದ ಪಾತ್ರ

6ನೇ ಪಂಚವರ್ಷೀಯ ಯೋಜನೆಯವರೆಗೆ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗಾಗಿಯೇ ಯಾವುದೇ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕವಾದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹಾಕಿಕೊಂಡಿರಲಿಲ್ಲ ಈ ಯೋಜನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗಾಗಿ ಕೆಲವೊಂದು ವಿಶೇಷ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹಾಕಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲಾಯಿತು.

- 1987ರಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳಾ ತರಬೇತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಉದ್ಯೋಗಕ್ಕೆ ನೆರವು ನೀಡುವ ಯೋಜನೆ(STEP)ಯನ್ನು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೆ ಉದ್ಯೋಗ ನೀಡುವ ಗುರಿಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತರಲಾಯಿತು.
- 1982ರಲ್ಲಿ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ಮಹಿಳೆ ಮತ್ತು ಮಕ್ಕಳ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯೋಜನೆ(DWCRA)
- 1988ರಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಮಹಿಳಾಯೋಜನೆ.

1995 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಇಂದಿರಾಗಾಂಧಿ ಮಹಿಳಾಯೋಜನೆ ಮತ್ತು 2001 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ವಯಂ ಸಿದ್ಧ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತಂದರು. ಸ್ವರ್ಣ ಜಯಂತಿ ಗ್ರಾಮಸ್ವರೋಜಗಾರ್ ಯೋಜನೆಯಡಿಲ್ಲಿ 40 ರಷ್ಟು ಪಲಾನುಭವಿಗಳು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರೇ ಆಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಇನ್ನಿತರ ಹಲವು ಯೋಜನೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಅದರ ಮೂಲಕ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರನ್ನು ಸಮಾಜದ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಹಿನಿಗೆ ತರಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಸ್ವಸಹಾಯಸಂಘಗಳು, ಮನೆಬೆಳಕುಯೋಜನೆ, ವಿಧವಾವೇತನ, ದೇವದಾಸಿ ಪುನರವಸತಿ ಯೋಜನೆ, ಭಾಗ್ಯಲಕ್ಷ್ಮಿಯೋಜನೆ ಇನ್ನು ಮುಂತಾದವು ಪಂಚಾಯತ ರಾಜ್ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೆ 1/3ರಷ್ಟು ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಸರಕಾರದ ಈ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳು ಆರ್ಥಿಕವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕವಾಗಿ ಸಶಕ್ತೀಕರಣ ವರ್ಷ ಎಂದು ಘೋಷಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ

ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣ ಮಾಡುವುದು ಹೇಗೆ ?

ಮಹಿಳೆಯು ಸುರಕ್ಷತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತಮ ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಹೊಂದುವುದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ, ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ, ಬೌದ್ಧಿಕ ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಮಾನಸಿಕ ಹಾಗೂ ದೈಹಿಕವಾಗಿ ಸಶಕ್ತಿಯಾಗಿ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿದೆ. ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಸುರಕ್ಷತೆಗೋಸ್ಕರ ಹಲವಾರು ಕಾನೂನುಗಳನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ ಆದರೆ ಈ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತರಲಾಗಿಲ್ಲ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳನ್ನು ಯಾವುದೇ ಪಕ್ಷಪಾತವಿಲ್ಲದೇ ಸಮರ್ಪಕವಾಗಿ ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತರುವ ತನಕ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ವಿರುದ್ಧದ ಅಪರಾಧಗಳು ನಿರಂತರವಾಗಿ ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಬಾರದು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ, ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಸುಲಭವಾಗಿ ದೊರೆಯಬೇಕು ಹಾಗೂ ಪುರುಷರೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸಮಾನ ಕೆಲಸಕ್ಕೆ ಸಮಾನ ವೇತನ ಕೊಡಬೇಕು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ತಮ್ಮ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ನಂಬಿಕೆಯನ್ನಿಟ್ಟು ತಮ್ಮ ಸ್ವಂತ ಗುರುತನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.ಪುರುಷ ಸಮಾಜವು ಮಹಿಳೆಯನ್ನು ಜೀವನದ ಅರ್ಧಾಂಗ ಎಂದು ಒಪ್ಪಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು ಮಹಿಳೆಯಿಲ್ಲದೆ ಪುರುಷನ ಜೀವನವು ಅಪೂರ್ಣ ಎಂಬ ಸತ್ಯವನ್ನು ಎಲ್ಲರೂ ತಿಳಿದುಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು ಉಪಸಂಹಾರ

ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕಾಲದಿಂದಲೂ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಸ್ಥಾನಮಾನ ಕುಂದುತ್ತಾ ಬಂದಿದೆ ಹಲವಾರು ಯೋಜನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹಾಕಿಕೊಂಡರೂ ಸಮಗ್ರವಾದ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಯಾಗಿಲ್ಲ ಕೆಲವು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ತರುವ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆ ಇದೆ ಚುನಾಯಿತ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗೆ ಅವರು ಅಗತ್ಯವಿರುವ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಲು ಅಗತ್ಯವಾದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಸ್ಥಳಾವಕಾಶದ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿದೆ. ಮಹಿಳಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪಂಚಾಯತಿ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೆ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ ವೇಗ ವರ್ಧಕವಾಗಿ ಕಾರ್ಯ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಈ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಯನ್ನು ಮತ್ತಷ್ಟು ತ್ವರಿತಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಮಹಿಳಾ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ ಮಸೂದೆಯನ್ನು ದುರ್ಬಲಗೊಳ್ಳದೇ ಕಾನೂನು ಅಗಬೇಕು ಅಲ್ಲದೇ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಂತೆ ಅಥವಾ ಮತದಾರರಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ವದೇಶ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರನ್ನು ಸ್ವಯಂ ಪ್ರೇರಣೆಯಿಂದ ಏಕೀಕರಿಸುವುದು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಮೇಲಿದೆ ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆ ನಿರೀಕ್ಷಿಸಿದರೂ ಸ್ವಯಂ ಶಾಶ್ವತವಾಗುವುದು ಎಂದು ನಾವು ಸಬಲೀಕರಣವನ್ನು ನೆನಪಿನಲ್ಲಿಟ್ಟುಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು. ಅವಕಾಶ ಮತ್ತು ಬೆಂಬಲ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ

ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೆ ಒದಗಿಸುವುದು(ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಇತರೇ ಸಮರ್ಥನೀಯ ಕ್ರಮ) ಲಿಂಗವನ್ನು ಸುಸ್ಥಿತಿಯಲ್ಲಿರಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯನ್ನು ಬದಲಾಯಿಸುವ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ

ಜವಾಹರಲಾಲ್ ನೆಹರು-“ಜನರನ್ನು ಜಾಗೃತಗೊಳಿಸಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಮೊದಲು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರನ್ನು ಜಾಗೃತಗೊಳಿಸಬೇಕು ಒಂದು ಸಲ ಮಹಿಳೆ ಪ್ರಗತಿ ಪಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಚಲಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಾರಂಭಿಸಿದರೆ ಇಡೀ ಕುಟುಂಬ ಹಳ್ಳಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ದೇಶದ ಪ್ರಗತಿಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ” ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯು ದೇಶದ ಪ್ರಗತಿಗೆ ಅತ್ಯವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಪರಾಮರ್ಶನ ಗ್ರಂಥಗಳು

ಡಾ. ಪ್ರೀತಿಶುಭಚಂದ್ರ : ಮಹಿಳಾ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ತಾತ್ವಿಕ ನೆಲೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಿಳಾ ಚಳುವಳಿಗಳು, ಪ್ರಸಾರಾಂಗ, ಕನ್ನಡ ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ, ಹಂಪಿ 2002

ಡಾ.ಹೆಚ್.ಟಿ.ಪೋತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಜಗನ್ನಾಥ ಸಿಂಧೆ: ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆ ಸವಾಲುಗಳು,ಪ್ರಕಾಶಕರು ತ್ರಿಮತಿ.ಲಲಿತ ಹೆಚ್ ಪೋತೆ, ಗುಲ್ಬರ್ಗ.

ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ : ಕೆ.ಎಂ ಸುರೇಶ್ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ ನಿಮ್ಮ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಾವಿಜೇತ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು

ಚಂದ್ರಪೂಜಾರಿ.ಎಂ. 2014 ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ: ಪಲ್ಲವ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ, ಚನ್ನಪಟ್ಟಣ

ಚಂದ್ರಗುರು ಬಿ.ಪಿ.2013, ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯ ಮಹಿಳೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಬಲೀಕರಣ, ಪ್ರಸಾರಾಂಗ, ಮೈಸೂರು.

ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣ ಹಾಗೂ ಸ್ವಸಹಾಯ ಗುಂಪುಗಳು,ಜಿ.ವೈ ಪಾಟೀಲ್

ಯೋಜನ ಮಾಸ ಪತ್ರಿಕೆ ಜೂನ್ 2012 ಸಮಾಚಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಸಾರ ಸಚಿವಾಲಯ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು.

ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆ ಅಂದು ಇಂದು. ಡಾ.ಜಿ.ಜವರೇಗೌಡ.

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Indian women and Society-Dr.M N Srinivas

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ರೇವಣ್ಣ.ಎಲ್.

ಸಂಶೋಧನಾ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿ

ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತ ವಿಭಾಗ,

ಮಹಾರಾಜ ಕಾಲೇಜು, ಮೈಸೂರು ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾನಿಲಯ, ಮೈಸೂರು-06.

ಸಾರಾಂಶ:

ಭವ್ಯ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟುಗಳ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯ ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳಿಗೆ ಶತಮಾನದ ಐತಿಹ್ಯವಿದೆ. ಆಧುನಿಕತೆಯ ರೂಪವನ್ನು ಬಹುತೇಕವಾಗಿ ಮೈಗೂಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಹಾಗೂ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಮರಮಾಚಿ ನಸುನಗುವಿನೊಡನೆ ಭಾರತದ ಪರಂಪರೆಯ ವೈಭವಿತ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಕಡೆಗಣಿಸುವ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟೇತರ ಜನಾಂಗಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಜನಾಂಗದ ಜನರು ತಮ್ಮ ನಿತ್ಯ ಜೀವನದ ಒಂದು ಭಾಗವಾಗಿ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಉಳಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಇಡೀ ಸಮಾಜವೇ ತಮ್ಮತ್ತ ತಿರುಗಿ ನೋಡುವಂತೆ ಸೂರೆಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಕುಲಕಸುಬುಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳು ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಜನಾಂಗಗಳು ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ಜೀವನಶೈಲಿ, ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ದೈಹಿಕ, ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದ ಕುಲಕಸುಬುಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿಕೊಂಡು ವೈವಿಧ್ಯಮಯ ಜೀವನವನ್ನು ಕಟ್ಟಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇಂತಹ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟುಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಇರಿಸಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಕಾಣುತ್ತೇವೆ. ಚಾಮರಾಜನಗರ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸೋಲಿಗ, ಜೇನುಕುರುಬ, ಕಾಡುಕುರುಬ, ಡೋಂಗಿ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳು ಕಾಡಂಚಿನ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಯೂರಿ ತಮ್ಮ ಬದುಕನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇಂತಹ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ಕೊಳ್ಳೇಗಾಲ ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕಿನಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಸಿರುವ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಸಮುದಾಯವು ಒಂದಾಗಿದೆ. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನಾಂಗವು ಪ್ರಾಚೀನತೆಯ ಕುರೂಹಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಐತಿಹ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಪಾರಂಪರಿಕ, ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ನೆನಪುಗಳನ್ನು ಕಣ್ಣುಬಿಡಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಒಂದು ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟತೆಯ ಜನಾಂಗವಾಗಿದೆ. ಹಿಂದೆ ತಮಿಳುನಾಡಿನ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿದ್ದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಚಾಮರಾಜನಗರ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯ ಕೊಳ್ಳೇಗಾಲ ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕಿನ ವಿವಿಧ ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. 'ಕಣಿ ಭವಿಷ್ಯ' ಹೇಳುವ ಮೂಲಕ 'ಭವಿಷ್ಯ ನುಡಿಯುವವರೆಂದು' ಗುರುತಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನಾಂಗದವರು ಕಣಿ ಭವಿಷ್ಯ, ಕವಡೆ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಮಾಟಮಂತ್ರ, ನಾಟ ವೈದ್ಯಪದ್ಧತಿ ಇವುಗಳನ್ನು ತಮ್ಮ ಕುಲಕಸುಬುಗಳನ್ನಾಗಿ ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಈ ಲೇಖನವು ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟಿನ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯನ್ನು ಅಧ್ಯಯನಿಸುವ ಉದ್ದೇಶವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದು, ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ ದ್ವಿತೀಯ ಮೂಲದ ದತ್ತಾಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಂತೆ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣಾತ್ಮಕ ಸ್ವರೂಪದ್ದಾಗಿದೆ.

ಮುಖ್ಯ ಪದಗಳು: ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು, ಕಣಿಯನ್, ಕುಲಕಸುಬು, ಕಣಿಭವಿಷ್ಯ, ನಾಟವೈದ್ಯಪದ್ಧತಿ, ಮಾಟಮಂತ್ರ.

ಪೀಠಿಕೆ :

ಪ್ರಪ್ರಥಮವಾಗಿ ರೋಮನ್ನರು ಜನಸಾಮಾನ್ಯರನ್ನು, ಸಮಾಜದ ವಿಭಾಗಗಳನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸಲು 'ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು' ಎಂಬ ಪದವನ್ನು ಬಳಸಿದರು. ಕಾಲಾನಂತರದಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಪದವು ಆರ್ಥಿಕವಾಗಿ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕವಾಗಿ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ಬಡವರು ಎಂಬ ಅರ್ಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿತು. ಕನ್ನಡದಲ್ಲಿ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯುವ ಈ ಪದವು ಇಂಗ್ಲೀಷ್‌ನಲ್ಲಿ 'ಟ್ರೈಬ್' ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿದೆ ಈ ಪದವು ಲ್ಯಾಟಿನ್ನಿನ 'ಟ್ರೈಬಸ್' ಎಂಬ ಪದದಿಂದ ಉಗಮಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಈ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಪದಕ್ಕೆ ಪರ್ಯಾಯವಾಗಿ ಮೂಲನಿವಾಸಿಗಳು, ಆದಿವಾಸಿಗಳು, ಸಂಚಾರಿ ಜನಾಂಗ, ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಜನಾಂಗ, ಅರಣ್ಯವಾಸಿಗಳು, ಗಿರಿಜನರು, ವನವಾಸಿಗಳು, ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡ, ಸರ್ವಜೀತನವಾದಿಗಳು ಎಂಬೆಲ್ಲಾ ಹೆಸರುಗಳಿಂದ ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ 700ಕ್ಕೂ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಮತ್ತು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ 50ಕ್ಕೂ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟುಗಳಿವೆ. ಈ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟುಗಳು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ವಿವಿಧ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳ ಬೆಟ್ಟ-ಗುಡ್ಡ, ಅರಣ್ಯ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಸಿ, ಅರಣ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ದೊರೆಯುವ ಉತ್ಪನ್ನಗಳನ್ನು ಉಪಯೋಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದಂತಹ ಜೀವನೋಪಾಯ ಮಾರ್ಗವನ್ನು ಕಂಡುಕೊಂಡು ಪರಿಸರದ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಅವಿನಾಭಾವ ಸಂಬಂಧವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿ ಕೆಳಸ್ಥರದ ಜೀವನವನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಭಾರತದ ಸಂವಿಧಾನವು 342ನೇ ವಿಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಜನರ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ 'ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡ'ಗಳೆಂದು ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಿಸಿದೆ. ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಿಕೊಟ್ಟಿದ್ದರೂ ಕೂಡ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಜನರು ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದಂತಹ ರೂಢಿ-ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯ, ಆಚಾರ-ವಿಚಾರ, ಆಹಾರ ಪದ್ಧತಿ, ಜೀವನ ಶೈಲಿ, ದೈವ, ಭಾಷೆ ಇನ್ನೂ ಮುಂತಾದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಕಟ್ಟುಪಾಡುಗಳನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ನಾಗರಿಕ ಸಮಾಜದಿಂದ ದೂರವೇ ಉಳಿದಿವೆ. ಇಂದಿಗೂ ಕೂಡ ಸಮಾಜದ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಹಿನಿಯ ಸಂಪರ್ಕವನ್ನೇ ಕಾಣದೇ ಸಮಾಜದಿಂದ ತಿರಸ್ಕರಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟು ಅಸಹನೀಯವಾದ ಜೀವನವನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟುಗಳು ಪಶ್ಚಿಮಾದ್ರಿ ಆವೃತವಾದ ದಟ್ಟವಾದ ಕಾಡು ಮತ್ತು ಅರಣ್ಯ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇಂತಹ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ಉತ್ತರ ಕನ್ನಡ, ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕನ್ನಡ, ಕೊಡಗು ಮತ್ತು ಮೈಸೂರು, ಚಾಮರಾಜನಗರ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿವೆ. ಇಂತಹ ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲವಾರು ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಜನಾಂಗಗಳು ನೆಲೆಸಿವೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಸೋಲಿಗರು, ಕಾಡುಕುರುಬ, ಜೇನುಕುರುಬ, ಯರವ, ಹಾಗೂ

ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಮಿತಿಗೆ ಒಳಪಟ್ಟಂತೆ ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಕೊಳ್ಳೇಗಾಲ ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾತ್ರ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಜನಾಂಗಗಳನ್ನು ಕಾಣುತ್ತೇವೆ. ಈ ಜನ ಸಮುದಾಯವು ಬೆಟ್ಟಗುಡ್ಡಗಳಲ್ಲಿ, ಕಾಡುಮೇಡುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ಬಯಲು ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸಿಸುತ್ತಾ, ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದ ಆಚಾರ-ವಿಚಾರ, ದೈವ, ಭಾಷಾ ಶೈಲಿ, ಮೂಲಪುರುಷ, ನಂಬಿಕೆ, ಆಚರಣೆ, ಉಡುಗೆ-ತೊಡುಗೆ, ಆಹಾರ, ನ್ಯಾಯ ಪದ್ಧತಿ ಹೊಂದಿರುವುದು ವೈಶಿಷ್ಟ್ಯವೇ ಸರಿ. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಸಮುದಾಯವು ಕವಡೆ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಮಾಟಮಂತ್ರ, ನಾಟಿ ವೈದ್ಯ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯನ್ನು ತಮ್ಮ ಕುಲಕಸುಬುಗಳನ್ನಾಗಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಜೀವನದ ಉಪ ಕಸುಬಾಗಿ ರೇಷ್ಮೆ ನೂಲು ಬಿಚ್ಚುವುದು, ಮಗ್ಗ ನೇಯುವುದು, ಕೃಷಿ, ಪಶುಸಂಗೋಪನೆಗಳನ್ನು ತಲೆಮಾರುಗಳಿಂದಲೂ ರೂಢಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಬದುಕನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವುದು ಕಾಣಿಸಿಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟಿನ ಐತಿಹ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಬೌಗೋಳಿಕ ನೆಲೆ:

ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಜನಾಂಗವು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಮಿತಿಗೆ ಒಳಪಟ್ಟಂತೆ ಚಾಮರಾಜನಗರ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯ ಕೊಳ್ಳೇಗಾಲ ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕಿನಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಸಿ ಬದುಕನ್ನು ಕಟ್ಟಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಪದದ ರೂಪಾಂತರವನ್ನು ದೃಷ್ಟಿಸಿದಾಗ ಕನ್ನಡ-ತಮಿಳು ದ್ವಿಭಾಷೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಸೇರಿದ್ದಾಗಿವೆ. ತಮಿಳು ಭಾಷೆಯಲ್ಲಿ 'ಕಣಿಯನ್' ಮತ್ತು 'ಕಣ್ಯನ್' ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿ; ಕನ್ನಡ ಭಾಷೆಯಲ್ಲೂ ಕೂಡ 'ಕಣಿಯನ್' ಮತ್ತು 'ಕಣ್ಯನ್' ನಾಮಾಂಕಿತಗಳಿಂದ ಹೆಸರಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಮತ್ತು ಕಣ್ಯನ್ ಎಂಬ ಪದಗಳು ಕಣಿ ಎಂಬ ಮೂಲಪದದಿಂದ ಹುಟ್ಟಿದವೆಂದು ನಿಸ್ಸಂಶಯವಾಗಿ ತಿಳಿಯುತ್ತದೆ. ಕಣಿ ಎಂದರೆ ಆಂಗ್ಲ ಭಾಷೆಯಲ್ಲಿ 'ಡಿವಿನೇಷನ್' (Divination) ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿದ್ದು, 'ಕಣಿ ಹೇಳುವುದು' ಮತ್ತು 'ಅಗೋಚರದ ಅರಿವು' ಎಂಬರ್ಥವಿದೆ ಇದರನ್ವಯ ಕಣಿ ಎಂಬುದು ಕಣಿಭವಿಷ್ಯ, ಕವಡೆಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಎಂಬೆಲ್ಲಾ ಅರ್ಥಗಳನ್ನು ಸೂಚಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಜನಾಂಗದ ಜನರು ಕಣಿಭವಿಷ್ಯ, ಕವಡೆಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಹಸ್ತಸಾಮುದ್ರಿಕಾವನ್ನು ಸ್ವೀಕರಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಈ ಹೆಸರು ಬಂದಿದೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಐತಿಹ್ಯ. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನಾಂಗದ ಜನರನ್ನು 'ದಾಸ', 'ತಿರುಕುಲ ದಾಸ' ಎಂಬ ಉಪನಾಮಗಳಿಂದಲೂ ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ. ತಿರು ಎಂಬ ಪದವು ತಮಿಳು ಭಾಷೆಯ ಮೂಲಪದವಾಗಿದ್ದು, ತಮಿಳಿನಲ್ಲಿ 'ತಿರು' ಎಂದರೆ 'ಶ್ರೀ' ಎಂಬರ್ಥವಿದೆ. ಇದರನ್ವಯ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಪ್ರತಿ ಶನಿವಾರವು ಹೆಗಲಿಗೆ ಜೋಳಿಗೆಯನ್ನೇರಿಸಿ ಅಂಗೈಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಿಕ್ಷಾಪಾತ್ರೆಯನ್ನಿಡಿದು "ಶಿವ ನಾರಾಯಣ ಗೋವಿಂದ... ಗೋವಿಂದ..." ಎಂದು ಕಂಠಾಘೋಷದಿಂದ ಭಕ್ತಿಯ ನಾಮ ಜಪಿಸುತ್ತಾ, ಮನೆ ಮನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸುತ್ತುತ್ತಾ, ಭಿಕ್ಷಾಟನೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಇವರ ನೆರೆಹೊರೆಯ ಜನರು ಈ ಜನಾಂಗದವರನ್ನು 'ದಾಸ'ರೆಂದು, 'ತಿರುಕುಲ ದಾಸ'ರೆಂದು ಕರೆಯುವುದು ವಾಡಿಕೆಯಾಗಿದೆ.

ಕರ್ನಾಟದ ಚಾಮರಾಜನಗರ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯ ಕೊಳ್ಳೇಗಾಲ ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾತ್ರ ನೆಲೆಸಿರುವ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಜನಾಂಗವು ತಮಿಳುನಾಡಿನ ಮೂಲದವರಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಮದ್ರಾಸ್ ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯದ(ಈಗಿನ ತಮಿಳುನಾಡು) ತಿರುವನೈಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ಕೊಯಮತ್ತೂರು ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಜನಾಂಗದವರು ಕಾಣಿಸಿಗುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಭಾಷಾವಾರು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ರಚನೆಯ ಪೂರ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಕೊಳ್ಳೇಗಾಲ ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕು ಕೊಯಮತ್ತೂರು ಜಿಲ್ಲಾ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿಗೆ ಸೇರಿದ್ದಾಗಿತ್ತು. 1956 ರಲ್ಲಿ ರಚನೆಯಾದ ಫಜಲ್ ಆಲಿ ಆಯೋಗದ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸಿನ ಮೇರೆಗೆ ಭಾಷೆಗಳ ಆಧಾರಿತವಾಗಿ ಭಾಷಾವಾರು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಪುನರ್ ರಚನೆಯ ಪರಿಣಾಮವಾಗಿ ಕೊಳ್ಳೇಗಾಲ ಪ್ರದೇಶವು ಮದ್ರಾಸ್ ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯದಿಂದ (ತಮಿಳುನಾಡಿನಿಂದ) ಬೇರ್ಪಟ್ಟು ಮೈಸೂರು ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯದ (ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ) ಪರಿದಿಯೊಳಗೆ ಸೇರಿಕೊಂಡಿತು. ಮೈಸೂರು ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯ ಕೊಳ್ಳೇಗಾಲ ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕಿಗೆ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸಿ ತಮಿಳುನಾಡಿನ ಮೂಲದವರಾದ ಕಣಿಯನ್(ಮೈಸೂರು ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯ ಕೊಳ್ಳೇಗಾಲ ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕಿಗೆ ಸೀಮಿತವಾದಂತೆ) ಜನಾಂಗವನ್ನು ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಎಂದು ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡಗಳ ಪಟ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸೇರಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಜನರು ಚಾಮರಾಜನಗರ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯ ಕೊಳ್ಳೇಗಾಲ ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕಿನ ಸೂರಾಪುರ, ಬೆಂಡರಹಳ್ಳಿ, ಮುಡಿಗುಂಡ, ಶಂಕನಪುರ ಮುತ್ತಾಪುರದಹುಂಡಿ, ಕೊಳ್ಳೇಗಾಲ ಪಟ್ಟಣ, ಗೊಬ್ಬಳಿಪುರ, ಟಗರಪುರ, ಆಲಹಳ್ಳಿ, ಹೊಸಮಾಲಂಗಿ, ಕಾಮಗೆರೆ(ಕೊಂಗರಹಳ್ಳಿ), ಕೋಡಿಪುರ, ಗುಂಡೇಗಾಲ ಸೇರಿದಂತೆ ಇನ್ನೂ ಹಲವು ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

1) ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನಾಂಗದ ಕುಲಕಸುಬಾಗಿ ಕಣಿ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರೀಯತೆ :

ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಜನರ ಜೀವನಕ್ಕೂ ಮತ್ತು ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟೇತರ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಜನರ ಜೀವನಕ್ಕೂ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸಗಳನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬಹುದು. ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟೇತರ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಜನರು ತಮ್ಮ ಜೀವನದ ಆಗುಹೋಗುಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಯಲು ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವನ್ನು ಅವಲಂಬಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಆಂಗ್ಲ ಭಾಷೆಯ ಆಸ್ಟ್ರೋಲಾಜಿ ಎಂಬುದಕ್ಕೆ ಕನ್ನಡದಲ್ಲಿ ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಕರೆಯಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಹೇಳುವವರನ್ನು ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷಿಗಳು ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇವರುಗಳು ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ವಿದ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡಿರುವವರಾಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ್ಯವನ್ನು ಹೇಳುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಜನರು ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ್ಯವನ್ನು ಹೇಳಲಾರರು. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಅವರುಗಳು ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷಿಗಳನ್ನು ಅವಲಂಬಿಸಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಜನಸಾಮಾನ್ಯರ ಬದುಕಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ್ಯವು ಒಂದು ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ನಂಬಿಕೆಯೂ ಮತ್ತು ಧೈರ್ಯವೂ ಆಗಿದೆ. "ಅಂತರಿಕ್ಷದಲ್ಲಿ ಗ್ರಹ ಮತ್ತು ನಕ್ಷತ್ರಗಳ ಸ್ಥಾನಗಳ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ನಡೆಸಿ, ಅವು ಬೀರುವ ಪ್ರಭಾವವನ್ನು ಲೆಕ್ಕಹಾಕುವ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ್ಯ" ಎನ್ನಲಾಗುವುದು. ಮಾನವನ ನಂಬಿಕೆಯ ತಳಹದಿಯ ಮೇಲೆ ನಿಂತಿರುವ ಈ ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವು ಮನುಷ್ಯನ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಮುಂದಿನ ಭವಿಷ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಮಾನವನ ಬದುಕಿನ ಮೇಲೆ ಸೂರ್ಯ, ಚಂದ್ರ, ನಕ್ಷತ್ರ ಮೊದಲಾದ ಗ್ರಹಗಳು ಪ್ರಭಾವ

ಬೀರುವುದನ್ನು ಇದು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ವಿಜ್ಞಾನವು ಎಷ್ಟೇ ಮುಂದುವರಿದರೂ ಜನ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯರಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ್ಯವು ಅಚಲವಾದ ನಂಬಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಉಳಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದೆ.

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಸಿರುವ ಜನ ಸಮೂಹಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳು ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕವಾಗಿ ಕಾಣುತ್ತವೆ. ನಾಗರಿಕ ಸಮಾಜದಿಂದ ದೂರವೇ ಉಳಿದು ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದಂತಹ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ತಲೆಮಾರುಗಳಿಂದ ರೂಢಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಬಂದಿವೆ. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಸಿರುವ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟುಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಸಮುದಾಯದೊಳಗೆ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟವಾದ ಭವಿಷ್ಯ ನುಡಿಯುವ ವಿದ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ಕರಗತ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಜನರ ಬದುಕಿನಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಸ್ಥಾನಮಾನ ಪಡೆದಿರುವ ಭವಿಷ್ಯ ನುಡಿಯುವುದು ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅತಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಪ್ರಚಲಿತದಲ್ಲಿದೆ. ಇದನ್ನು ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕ ಕುಲಕಸುಬನ್ನಾಗಿ ಹಾಗೂ ವಂಶಪಾರಂಪರ್ಯ ವೃತ್ತಿಯನ್ನಾಗಿ ಉಳಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಬಂದಿರುವ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನಾಂಗವು ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ ಕಾಣಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಜನಾಂಗವು ಕಣಿಭವಿಷ್ಯ ನುಡಿಯುವುದನ್ನು ಕುಲಕಸುಬನ್ನಾಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಬದುಕುತ್ತಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಕಾಣುತ್ತೇವೆ. ಪ್ರಕೃತಿ ಆರಾಧಕರಾಗಿರುವ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಜನರು ಸಮುದ್ರದ ದಡದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಿಗುವ ಕವಡೆಗಳನ್ನು ದೇವರೆಂದು ಭಾವಿಸಿ ಕವಡೆಯಿಂದ ಭವಿಷ್ಯ ನುಡಿಯುವ ಕಲೆಯನ್ನು ಹಿರಿಯರಿಂದ ಕಲಿತು ಇಂದಿಗೂ ತಮ್ಮ ಜೀವನದ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿ ರೂಢಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವುದು ಆಶ್ಚರ್ಯವೆನಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ತಮ್ಮ ಸಮುದಾಯದೊಳಗೆ ನಡೆಯುವ ಶುಭ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳಾದ ಜನನ, ನಾಮಕರಣ, ವಿವಾಹ, ಮನೆ ಕಟ್ಟುವುದು, ಮರಣ, ತಿಥಿ, ಯಶಸ್ಸು-ಅಪಯಶಸ್ಸು, ಮಾಟ-ಮಂತ್ರ, ಬದುಕಿನ ಸಫಲತೆಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಜನಾಂಗದ ಹಿರಿಯರು ನುಡಿಯುವ ಭವಿಷ್ಯವನ್ನು ಜನರು ಅಗಾಧವಾಗಿ ನಂಬುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಅವಲಂಬಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಕಣಿಭವಿಷ್ಯವು ಈ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರ ಬದುಕಿನ ಪ್ರತಿಘಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಜೊತೆಗಾರನಂತೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಮಾನವನ ಮನಸ್ಸಿನ ಆಲೋಚನೆಗೆ ಮಾರ್ಗವಿದ್ದಂತೆ. ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಅನೇಕ ರಹಸ್ಯ ವಿಷಯಗಳು ಅಡಕವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಭವಿಷ್ಯ ನುಡಿಯುವುದು ಒಂದು ರೀತಿಯಾದ ಅತೀಂದ್ರಿಯ ಜ್ಞಾನವಾಗಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡಲು ಪರಿಶ್ರಮ, ತಾಳ್ಮೆ, ಶುದ್ಧತೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಅವಶ್ಯಕ. ಭವಿಷ್ಯ ತಿಳಿಸುವ ಕಲೆಯು ವಂಶಪಾರಂಪರಿಕವಾಗಿ ಕೆಲವರಿಗೆ ಬಳುವಳಿಯಾಗಿ ಬಂದಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಅಂತಹವರು ಮಾತ್ರ ಕಣಿಶಾಸ್ತ್ರೀಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥೈಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದು. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಭವಿಷ್ಯ ನುಡಿಯುವುದನ್ನು ತಮ್ಮ ಕುಲಕಸುಬಾಗಿ ಆದಿಮ ಕಾಲದಿಂದಲೂ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಬರುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರಲ್ಲಿ ಹಲವರು ಭವಿಷ್ಯ ಹೇಳುವುದರಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಣಿತರಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ನಗರ, ಪಟ್ಟಣ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಿಗೆ ತೆರಳಿ ಅಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಸಿ, ಭವಿಷ್ಯ ಹೇಳುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಕಣಿಭವಿಷ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಪಂಚಾಂಗ ಭವಿಷ್ಯವನ್ನು ಉತ್ತುಂಗಕ್ಕೆರಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಭವಿಷ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವನ್ನು ಬಲವಾಗಿ ನಂಬಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಒಂದೊಂದು ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಗಳು ವೈವಿಧ್ಯಮಯವಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸುವ ನಿಯಮಗಳು ಕೂಡ ಅಷ್ಟೇ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟವೆನ್ನಬಹುದು.

ಒಂಟಿಕೊಪ್ಪಲು ಪಂಚಾಂಗದ ವಿಶೇಷತೆ :

ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಪಂಚಾಂಗವು ದೇವರ ಸಮಾನ. ಪಂಚಾಂಗ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ನೋಡುವುದು ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ್ಯದ ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಕಾರವಾಗಿದೆ. ಪಂಚಾಂಗ ನೋಡುವಲ್ಲಿ ಅನುಭವವಿದ್ದರೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಅದನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥೈಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಭವಿಷ್ಯ ಹೇಳಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯ ಪಂಚಾಂಗಕ್ಕೆ ವಿಶೇಷವಾದ ಸ್ಥಾನ ನೀಡಿರುವ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಜನನ, ನಾಮಕರಣ, ವಿವಾಹ, ಮರಣ, ತಿಥಿ, ಶುಭಕಾರ್ಯ ಮೊದಲಾದ ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪಂಚಾಂಗದ ಮೂಲಕ ತಿಥಿ, ಕಾಲ, ವಾರ, ನಕ್ಷತ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿದು ಕಾರ್ಯವನ್ನು ಆರಂಭಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನಾಂಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಭವಿಷ್ಯ ಹೇಳುವವರ ಮನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾತ್ರ ಪಂಚಾಂಗವಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಪಂಚಾಂಗವನ್ನು ತಮ್ಮ ದೇವರ ಕೋಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿಟ್ಟು ಪ್ರತಿನಿತ್ಯವು ಪೂಜೆ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಪ್ರತಿ ವರ್ಷ ಯುಗಾದಿ ಹಬ್ಬದಂದು ದೇವರ ಮುಂದೆ ಹೊಸ ಪಂಚಾಂಗವಿಟ್ಟು, ವಿಶೇಷ ಪೂಜೆ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಪಂಚಾಂಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಪಾರವಾದ ನಂಬಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿಶ್ವಾಸವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಪಂಚಾಂಗ ನೋಡದೆ ಯಾವುದೇ ಶುಭಕಾರ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಈ ರೀತಿಯಾದ ನಂಬಿಕೆಯು ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮನೋಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ತೋರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಪಂಚಾಂಗ ನೋಡುವುದನ್ನು ಒಂದು ವೃತ್ತಿಯಾಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಮಗು ಹುಟ್ಟಿದ ಘಳಿಗೆಯ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ರಾಶಿ, ನಕ್ಷತ್ರ, ಲಗ್ನ, ಗೋತ್ರ ಇವುಗಳನ್ನು ಪಂಚಾಂಗದ ಮೂಲಕ ಲೆಕ್ಕಾಚಾರ ಹಾಕಿ ಕಾಲ ನಿರ್ಣಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ. ರಾಶಿಕುಂಡಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ನವಾಂಶ ಕುಂಡಲಿಗಳನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಿ ಹುಟ್ಟಿದ ಘಳಿಗೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾವ ಯಾವ ಗ್ರಹಗಳು ಯಾವ ಯಾವ ಮನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಇವೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ತಿಳಿದು ಅದರ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಭವಿಷ್ಯದ ಫಲಗಳನ್ನು ಹೇಳುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಜನನ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಗ್ರಹಗಳು ಹೇಗೆ ಹರಡಿಕೊಂಡಿವೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ತಿಳಿದು ಆ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯ ಜೀವನದ ಮೇಲೆ ಆಗುವ ಒಳ್ಳೆಯ ಹಾಗೂ ಕೆಟ್ಟ ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಮಗುವು ಬೆಳೆದಂತೆ ಗ್ರಹಗಳು ಬೇರೆ ಬೇರೆ ಮನೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಚಲಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಮಾನವನ ಬದುಕಿನ ಮೇಲೆ ಗ್ರಹಗಳ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಉಂಟಾಗುತ್ತದೆಂದು ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನಾಂಗದ ಪಂಡಿತರು ಹೇಳುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಗುರು, ಶುಕ್ರ, ಗ್ರಹಗಳ ಇಂತಹ ದೆಸೆಯಿಂದ ಶುಭ ಉಂಟಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಪಂಚಾಂಗವು ಕಾಲ, ತಿಂಗಳು, ತಿಥಿ, ದಿನ ವಾರ, ನಕ್ಷತ್ರ, ಇವುಗಳನ್ನು ಆಧರಿಸಿ ಮುಂದಿನ ಭವಿಷ್ಯವನ್ನು ವಿವರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಪಂಚಾಂಗದ ಕಾಲವನ್ನು ಅವಲಂಬಿಸಿದ ಇವರು ಜನನ, ವಿವಾಹ ಮೂಹೂರ್ತಗಳನ್ನು ಗೊತ್ತುಪಡಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.

ಭವಿಷ್ಯ ಸೂಚಿತ ಕವಡೆ (ಕವಡೆ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ):

ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನಾಂಗದವರಲ್ಲಿ ಪಂಚಾಂಗಕ್ಕಿರುವಂತೆ ಕವಡೆ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಕ್ಕೂ ವಿಶೇಷ ಮಹತ್ವವಿದೆ.ಇದು ಪಂಚಾಂಗಕ್ಕಿಂತ ವಿಭಿನ್ನವಾದ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ.ಪಂಚಾಂಗವು ನಕ್ಷತ್ರ ರಾಶಿಗಳ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ರೂಪಿತವಾದರೆ ಕವಡೆ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವು ನವಗ್ರಹಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ರೂಪಿತವಾಗಿದೆ.ಕವಡೆಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವೆಂದರೆ ಕವಡೆಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಫಲಾಫಲಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಯುವುದು.ಕವಡೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನೂರಾರು ಜಾತಿಯ ಕವಡೆಗಳಿವೆ. ಕವಡೆಗಳು ಕಡಲ ಮೃದ್ವುಗಳ ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಭೇದ.ಕವಡೆಗಳ ಬಣ್ಣ, ಆಕಾರ, ಗಾತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸವಿರುತ್ತದೆ.ಸಮುದ್ರದ ತೀರದಲ್ಲಿ ಇವು ಸಿಗುತ್ತವೆ. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಒಂದೇ ಗಾತ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಒಂದೇ ಆಕಾರದ ಒಂಭತ್ತು ಕವಡೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕವಡೆ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಹೇಳಲು ಉಪಯೋಗಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಈ ಒಂಭತ್ತು ಕವಡೆಗಳು ಒಂಭತ್ತು ಗ್ರಹಗಳ ಸಂಕೇತ.ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಕವಡೆ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದಿಂದ ಅರ್ಥ ಹುಡುಕುವ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಸಮಸ್ಯೆ ಹೇಳಲು ಬಂದ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಪೂರ್ವ ಅಥವಾ ಉತ್ತರ ದಿಕ್ಕಿಗೆ ಎದುರಾಗಿ ಕುಳಿತುಕೊಳ್ಳುವಂತೆ ಹೇಳುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆ ಕೇಳಲು ಬಂದ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗೆ ಮನಸ್ಸಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾವುದಾದರೂ ಇಷ್ಟದೈವವನ್ನು ನೆನೆದು ಕವಡೆ ಬಿಡಲು ಸೂಚಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಅವರ ಕೈಯಿಂದ ಮೂರು ಸಲ ಕವಡೆ ಬಿಡಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಒಂಭತ್ತು ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯ ಒಳಗೆ ಬಿದ್ದರೆ ಅದನ್ನು ಕಳೆಯುವಂತಿಲ್ಲ. ಒಂಭತ್ತಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ ಬಂದಿದ್ದರೆ ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂಭತ್ತನ್ನು ಕಳೆಯಬೇಕು.ಉಳಿದ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಬಂದು ಕುಳಿತ ಕಾಲಕ್ಕೆ ಯಾವ ಗ್ರಹ ಇದೆ ಎಂದು ತಿಳಿದು ಅದರ ಮೇಲೆ ಫಲ ಹೇಳುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಒಂದು, ಮೂರು, ಐದು, ಏಳು, ಒಂಭತ್ತು ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ ಬಂದರೆ ಒಳಿತಾಗುವುದೆಂದು ನಂಬಿಕೆ.ಒಂಭತ್ತು ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ನವಗ್ರಹಗಳಿಗೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿ ಫಲಾಫಲಗಳನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಕುಲದೇವರ ಆಧಾರಿತವಾಗಿ ಪೂಜೆ ಮತ್ತು ಶಿಷ್ಟಾಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಪರಿಹಾರಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಆಧುನಿಕತೆಯ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಜೀವನದ ನಡುವೆಯೂ ಪುರಾತನ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ಉಳಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವುದು ಸಂಶೋಧಕರಲ್ಲಿ ಆಶ್ಚರ್ಯವನ್ನು ಮೂಡಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಓಲೆಗರಿ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ :

ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟಿನ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಓಲೆಗರಿ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವೂ ಒಂದಾಗಿದೆ.ಓಲೆಗರಿಂದ ರಚಿತವಾದ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವನ್ನು ಓಲೆಗರಿ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಎನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಇದನ್ನು ತಾಳೆಗರಿಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಶಿಲ್ಪಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಚಿಂತಾಮಣಿ ಎಂದು ವಿವಿಧ ಹೆಸರುಗಳಿಂದ ಇಲ್ಲಿನ ಜನರು ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಇದೊಂದು ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ.ಓಲೆಗರಿ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಹೇಳುವುದರಲ್ಲಿ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಪರಿಣಿತರು.ಓಲೆಗರಿಯ ಕಟ್ಟು ಪುಸ್ತಕ ರೂಪದಲ್ಲಿರುತ್ತದೆ.ಒಂದು ಗರಿಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಚಿತ್ರಗಳಿದ್ದರೆ ಮತ್ತೊಂದು ಗರಿಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಫಲದ ವಿವರಗಳಿರುತ್ತವೆ.ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಈ ಚಿತ್ರಗಳು ದೇವರ ಚಿತ್ರಗಳಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಎಷ್ಟೋ ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೇವಲ ಗೊಂಬೆಯ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಒಳ್ಳೆಯ ಹಾಗೂ ಕೆಟ್ಟ ಫಲಗಳನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯಿರುವ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯಿಂದ ಒಂದು ದಬ್ಬಳದಿಂದ ತಾಳೆಗರಿಯ ಓಲೆಯನ್ನು ಮುಟ್ಟಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಏನು ಬರೆದಿದೆಯೋ ಅದರ ಫಲಾಫಲಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ಪರಿಹಾರವನ್ನು ಹೇಳುತ್ತಾರೆ.

ಹಸ್ತ ಸಾಮುದ್ರಿಕೆ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ:

ಹಸ್ತರೇಖೆಗಳ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಭವಿಷ್ಯ ಹೇಳುವುದನ್ನು ಹಸ್ತ ಸಾಮುದ್ರಿಕಾ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವೆನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಮಾನವನ ದೇಹದ ಬಹುಮುಖ್ಯ ಅಂಗವಾಗಿರುವ ಕೈಯೊಳಗಿನ ಹಸ್ತದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ರೇಖೆಗಳನ್ನು ಈ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ ಪರಿಗಣಿಸಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಸ್ತರೇಖೆಗಳ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವು ಕೈ ಮತ್ತು ಬೆರಳುಗಳನ್ನು ಆಧರಿಸಿದ್ದು ಮನುಷ್ಯನ ಜೀವನದ ಆಗುಹೋಗುಗಳನ್ನು, ಆಯಸ್ಸು-ಗಂಡಾಂತರ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಗತಿಗಳನ್ನು ವಿವರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.ಹಸ್ತರೇಖೆಗಳು ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟವಾದ ಗುಣಲಕ್ಷಣಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯ ಹಸ್ತರೇಖೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸವಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ರೇಖೆಗಳನ್ನಾಧರಿಸಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯೊಬ್ಬನ ಭವಿಷ್ಯ, ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಂದೊದಗುವ ಅಪಾಯವನ್ನು, ಮುಂದೆ ನಡೆಯುವ ವಿದ್ಯಮಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಗುರುತಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಹಸ್ತದೊಳಗಿರುವ ರೇಖೆಗಳಿಗೆ ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಸ್ಥಾನಮಾನಗಳಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಆಯಾ ರೇಖೆಗಳು ಸ್ವಭಾವಿಕವಾಗಿ ಅವುಗಳ ಸ್ಥಾನದಲ್ಲಿದ್ದರೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಆ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯ ಭವಿಷ್ಯವು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ರೇಖೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸಗಳಿದ್ದರೆ ಈ ರೀತಿಯ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳ ಗುಣ-ಸ್ವಭಾವಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಆತನ ಭವಿಷ್ಯದಲ್ಲಾಗುವ ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳು ಭಿನ್ನವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಜನಪದರಿಗೆ ಈ ಹಸ್ತರೇಖಾ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಪೂರ್ಣ ನಂಬಿಕೆಯಿದೆ.

ಹಸ್ತರೇಖೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜೀವನರೇಖೆ, ವಿಧಿರೇಖೆ, ಆರೋಗ್ಯರೇಖೆ, ಧನರೇಖೆ, ವಿದ್ಯಾರೇಖೆ, ಅಧ್ಯಾತ್ಮರೇಖೆ, ಅನ್ನರೇಖೆ, ದಾಂಪತ್ಯರೇಖೆ, ಸಂತಾನರೇಖೆ ಹೀಗೆ ಹಲವು ರೇಖೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ವಿವರಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇವುಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಮನುಷ್ಯನ ಗ್ರಹಗತಿಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಯುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಹಸ್ತರೇಖೆಗಳನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸಿ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಹೇಳಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಅವರಿಗೆ ಅನುಭವವಿರಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ರೇಖೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ವಲ್ಪ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸವಿದ್ದರೂ ಅದು ಬೇರೆ ರೇಖೆಯೆಂದು ಗುರುತಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ.ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಗಂಡಸರಿಗೆ ಬಲಗೈ ಮತ್ತು ಹೆಂಗಸರಿಗೆ ಎಡಗೈ ಹಸ್ತಗಳನ್ನು ನೋಡಿ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಹೇಳುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಹಸ್ತ ನೋಡಿದ ತಕ್ಷಣ ಒಳ್ಳೆಯ ಫಲಗಳನ್ನು ಹೇಳುವಷ್ಟು ಸುಲಭವಾಗಿ ಕೆಟ್ಟ ಫಲಗಳನ್ನು ಹೇಳುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿದ್ದರೆ ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ಸೂಕ್ತವಾದ ಪರಿಹಾರಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಬೆರಳುಗಳ ಕೊನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಶಂಖ-ಚಿಕ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸಿ ಅವುಗಳು ಎಷ್ಟಿವೆಯೆಂದು ತಿಳಿದು ಅವುಗಳ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಮನುಷ್ಯನ ಭವಿಷ್ಯವನ್ನು ವಿವರಿಸುವರು.

ಅಂಗ ಸಾಮುದ್ರಿಕ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ :

ಮಾನವನ ದೇಹದ ಅಂಗಗಳ ಲಕ್ಷಣಗಳನ್ನು ಕುರಿತು ಹೇಳುವುದೇ ಅಂಗ ಸಾಮುದ್ರಿಕ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ. ಇದು ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ್ಯದ ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಕಾರ. ಇದರಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಅಂಗ ಸಾಮುದ್ರಿಕ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಪುರುಷ ಅಂಗ ಸಾಮುದ್ರಿಕ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವೆಂದಿದೆ. ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಸಾಮುದ್ರಿಕ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರನ್ನು ಮಾತ್ರ ಕುರಿತು ಹೇಳಬಹುದು. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರಲ್ಲಿ ನಾಲ್ಕು ಜಾತಿಯ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಪದ್ಮಿನಿ, ಶಂಕಿನಿ, ಹಸ್ತಿನಿ, ಚಿತ್ತಿನಿ. ಇವು ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಲಕ್ಷಣಗಳನ್ನು ಕುರಿತು ಹೇಳುವ ಜಾತಿಗಳು. ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರು ಯಾವ ರೀತಿ ಇದ್ದರೆ ಅದೃಷ್ಟ-ದುರಾದೃಷ್ಟ ಎಂದು ಈ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಜಾತಿಗಳಿಂದ ಗುರುತಿಸಬಹುದು. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಹೇಳುವಂತೆ ಹುಬ್ಬುಗಳು ಕೂಡಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ವಿವಾಹಕ್ಕೆ ಯೋಗ್ಯಲ್ಲ. ಹಣೆ ಅಗಲವಿದ್ದರೆ ಬೇಗನೆ ವಿಧವೆಯಾಗುತ್ತಾಳೆ. ಕಾಲು ನೆಲದ ಮೇಲಿಟ್ಟಾಗ ಕಿರುಬೆರಳು ಮೇಲಕ್ಕೆದ್ದರೆ ಆ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರು ವಿವಾಹಕ್ಕೆ ತಕ್ಕವರಲ್ಲ. ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಅಂಗಸಾಮುದ್ರಿಕ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರನ್ನು ಕುರಿತು ಅನೇಕ ರೀತಿಯ ಲಕ್ಷಣಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಪುರುಷರ ಅಂಗ ಸಾಮುದ್ರಿಕ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವು ಪುರುಷರ ಅಂಗ ಲಕ್ಷಣಗಳನ್ನು ಕುರಿತು ವಿವರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗೆ: ಕಿವಿ ಅಗಲವಿದ್ದರೆ ಶ್ರೇಯಸ್ಸು, ಹಣೆ ಅಗಲವಿದ್ದರೆ ಅದೃಷ್ಟ, ಮೂಗು ಉದ್ದವಾಗಿದ್ದರೆ ಐಶ್ವರ್ಯವಂತ ಮೊದಲಾದ ನಂಬಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕುರಿತು ಈ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

2) ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರ ಯಂತ್ರ-ತಂತ್ರ :

ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಯಂತ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ತಾವೇ ಸ್ವತಃ ತಯಾರು ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ. ತಾಮ್ರದ ತಗಡಿನಿಂದ ತಯಾರಿಸುವ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಯಂತ್ರದ ಮೇಲೆ ದೇವರ ಚಿತ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ಬರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಅವುಗಳು ಗಣಪತಿ, ಭೈರವ, ಮಾರುತಿ, ನರಸಿಂಹ ಮೊದಲಾದ ದೇವರುಗಳ ಚಿತ್ರಗಳಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಈ ಯಂತ್ರವನ್ನು ಮಕ್ಕಳು ಬೆಚ್ಚಿಬಿದ್ದಿದ್ದರೆ, ಭಯಪಟ್ಟಿದ್ದರೆ, ಮೈ-ಕೈ ನೊವಾಗಿದ್ದರೆ, ಜ್ವಾನ್ ತಪ್ಪಿದ್ದರೆ, ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಸರಿಯಿಲ್ಲದಿದ್ದರೆ ಮಂತ್ರಿಸಿ ವಿಭೂತಿಯನ್ನಿಟ್ಟು ಕಟ್ಟುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಯಂತ್ರ-ಮಂತ್ರಗಳಿಂದಲೇ ಅನೇಕ ಕಾಯಿಲೆಗಳನ್ನು ಗುಣಪಡಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ದೇಹ ಮತ್ತು ಮನಸ್ಸಿನ ಮೇಲೆ ಈ ಯಂತ್ರ ಪರಿಣಾಮ ಬೀರುತ್ತದೆಯೆಂದು ಅಲ್ಲಿ ಬರುವ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳು ನಂಬುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಪಂಡಿತರು ಮಂತ್ರವನ್ನು ಹೇಳುತ್ತಾ ಯಂತ್ರ ಕಟ್ಟುವ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯು ರೂಢಿಯಲ್ಲಿದೆ. ಹೀಗೆ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಅಪಾಯದಿಂದ ಕಾಪಾಡುವ ಅಥವಾ ಅಪಾಯವನ್ನು ತಡೆಯುವ ಗುಣವನ್ನು ಈ ಯಂತ್ರ-ಮಂತ್ರ ಹೊಂದಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಕೈ ಕಾಲು ಉಳುಕಿದ್ದರೆ ಕಬ್ಬಿಣದ ಸರಳಿನಿಂದಲೂ ಮಂತ್ರ ಹಾಕುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಪಂಡಿತರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಇದು ಸರ್ವರೋಗಕ್ಕೂ ಮಂತ್ರ, ಅಷ್ಟೇ ಅಲ್ಲದೆ ಮಕ್ಕಳ ಫಲಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಸಂತಾನ ಗೋಪಾಲ ಯಂತ್ರ, ಮದುವೆ ಆಗುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ಮಾಂಗಲ್ಯ ಯಂತ್ರ, ಮಕ್ಕಳ ಆರೋಗ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಬಾಲಗ್ರಹ ಯಂತ್ರ - ಹೀಗೆ ವಿವಿಧ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳಿಗಾಗಿ ಯಂತ್ರವನ್ನು ಕಟ್ಟುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಎಲ್ಲ ಜಾತಿಯ ಜನ ಇವರ ಬಳಿ ಯಂತ್ರ ಕಟ್ಟಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇವರ ಬಳಿಗೆ ಬರುವವರು ಈ ಯಂತ್ರ-ಮಂತ್ರಗಳಿಂದ ಕಾಯಿಲೆಗಳು ವಾಸಿಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ಬಲವಾಗಿ ನಂಬುತ್ತಾರೆ.

ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರ ಮಾಟ-ಮಂತ್ರ:

ಜನಪದರು ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯ ಆರಾಧಕರು. ಮಾನವನು ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಅಗೋಚರ ಶಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಒಲಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಹಲವು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾ ಬಂದಿದ್ದಾನೆ. ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯ ಅನೇಕ ರಹಸ್ಯ ವಿಷಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾಟವು ಒಂದಾಗಿದೆ. ಒಳಿತಿಗಾಗಿ, ಕೆಡುಕಿಗಾಗಿ ಮಾಡುವ ಮಾಟದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಜನಪದರಿಗೆ ಬಲವಾದ ನಂಬಿಕೆಯಿದೆ. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಮಾಟ ಮಾಡುವುದರಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧರು. ಇದೂ ಸಹ ಅವರ ಒಂದು ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕ ಕಸುಬಾಗಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಇತ್ತೀಚೆಗೆ ಮಾಟ ಮಾಡುವ ಕ್ರಿಯೆಯು ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರಲ್ಲಿ ಬಹಳ ಕಡಿಮೆಯಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆಯೆಂದು ಹೇಳಬಹುದು. ಮಾಟ ಮಾಡುವ ವಿಧಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಇವರು ಯಾರಿಗೂ ತಿಳಿಸದೆ ರಹಸ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಕಾಪಾಡಿಕೊಂಡು ಬರುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ವಂಶಪಾರಂಪರವಾಗಿ ಬಂದಿರುವ ಈ ಮಾಟ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯನ್ನು ತಂದೆಯಾದವನು ತನ್ನ ಮಗನಿಗೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಕಲಿಸುತ್ತಾನೆ, ಇತರರಿಗೆ ತಿಳಿಸುವುದಿಲ್ಲ.

ಇತ್ತೀಚೆಗೆ ಮಾಟ ಮಾಡುವುದು ಕಾನೂನು ರೀತ್ಯಾ ಅಪರಾಧವಾದ್ದರಿಂದ ಆ ಕೆಲಸವನ್ನು ಕೈ ಬಿಟ್ಟಿರುವುದಾಗಿ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಆದರೆ ಯಾವ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯಾದರೂ ಕೇಡಿಗೆ ಒಳಗಾಗಿದ್ದರೆ ಅವನ ಒಳಿತಿಗಾಗಿ ಮಾಟವನ್ನು ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇದನ್ನು 'ತಡೆ ಹೊಡೆಯುವುದು' ಎನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಮೂರು ಸಣ್ಣ ಕುಡಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಬಿಳಿಯ ಬಟ್ಟೆಯಿಂದ ಮುಚ್ಚಿ ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ದಾರವನ್ನು ಕಟ್ಟಿ ಅರಿಶಿನ-ಕುಂಕುಮವಿಟ್ಟು ಮಂತ್ರ ಹೇಳಿ ಪೂಜಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಹೀಗೆ ಮಾಡುವುದರಿಂದ ಮಾಟ ನಿವಾರಣೆಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬ ನಂಬಿಕೆ. ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಅಪಾಯದಿಂದ ಕಾಪಾಡಲು ಮಾತ್ರ ತಡೆಯೋಡೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಅನೇಕ ರಹಸ್ಯ ವಿಷಯಗಳನ್ನೊಳಗೊಂಡಿರುವ ಈ ಮಾಟವು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಜಗತ್ತಿಗೆ ಒಂದು ಸವಾಲಾಗಿ ಪರಿಣಮಿಸಿದೆ.

3) ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನಪದರ ನಾಟವೈದ್ಯ ಪದ್ಧತಿ :

ನಾಟ ವೈದ್ಯ ತಯಾರು ಮಾಡುವುದು ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರ ಮತ್ತೊಂದು ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕ ವೃತ್ತಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಅನೇಕ ಕಾಯಿಲೆಗಳಿಗೆ ವೈದ್ಯ ನೀಡುವುದರಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರವೀಣರು. ಇವರು ಪ್ರಕೃತಿದತ್ತವಾಗಿ ದೊರೆಯುವ ಗಿಡಮೂಲಿಕೆಗಳಿಂದ ಸ್ವತಃ ಔಷಧಿ ತಯಾರು ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ. ನಾಡಿ ಜ್ವಾನ್ ನೋಡುವುದರಲ್ಲಿ ಅನುಭವಿಗಳು. ಜ್ವರ, ಶೀತ, ಕೆಮ್ಮು, ತಲೆನೋವು - ಇಂತಹ ಅನೇಕ ಕಾಯಿಲೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಈ ವೈದ್ಯ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯ ಮೂಲಕ ಮಾರ್ಗೋಪಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ಕಂಡುಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇವರು ಔಷಧಿ ನೀಡುವ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯು

ಸರಳವಾಗಿದೆ.ರೋಗಿಗಳನ್ನು ಗುಣಪಡಿಸುವ ರೀತಿ ಸಹಜವೂ ಆಗಿದೆ.ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಇವರಲ್ಲಿ ವೈದ್ಯ ಗೊತ್ತಿರುವವರನ್ನು ಪಂಡಿತರು ಎಂದು ಗೌರವದಿಂದ ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಇವರು ರೋಗಗಳ ಲಕ್ಷಣಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ನೀಡುವ ಚಿಕಿತ್ಸೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕನ್ನಡ ಪದ್ಯಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ನೆನಪಿನಲ್ಲಿಟ್ಟುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಹೀಗೆ ವೈದ್ಯ ಪದ್ಧತಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಇನ್ನು ಅನೇಕ ಪದ್ಯಗಳಿವೆ. ಈ ರೀತಿ ಪದ್ಯಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ವೈದ್ಯ ನೀಡುವುದು ಸಿದ್ಧರಲ್ಲಿದೆ.ಸಿದ್ಧರು ನೀಡುವ ಔಷಧಿ 'ಸಿದ್ಧೌಷಧಿ' ಎಂದೇ ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧವಾಗಿದೆ.ಸಿದ್ಧರ ಔಷಧಿ ತಮಿಳು ಭಾಷೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪದ್ಯಗಳ ರೂಪದಲ್ಲಿವೆ.ಬಹುಶಃ ಈ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರ ಮೇಲಾಗಿರಬಹುದು.

ಗಾಯವಾದರೆ : ಪೊಪ್ಪುಡಿ ಚಕ್ಕೆಯನ್ನು ಪುಡಿ ಮಾಡಿ ಕೊಬ್ಬರಿ ಎಣ್ಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹಾಕಿದರೆ ಗಾಯ ವಾಸಿಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ವಾಂತಿ : ಕಡಜದ ಗೂಡಿನ ಮಣ್ಣನ್ನು ಅರೆದು ನೀರಲ್ಲಿ ಶೋಧಿಸಿ ಜೇನುತುಪ್ಪವನ್ನು ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಬೆರೆಸಿ ನವಿಲುಗರಿಯನ್ನು ದೀಪದಲ್ಲಿ ಸುಟ್ಟು ಆ ಬೂದಿಯನ್ನು ಈ ಮೂರರಲ್ಲಿ ಬೆರೆಸಿ ಸ್ವಲ್ಪ ನೆಕ್ಕಿದರೆ ವಾಸಿಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಬೇಕೆನಿಸಿದರೆ ಸ್ವಲ್ಪ ನಿಂಬೆಹಣ್ಣಿನ ರಸವನ್ನು ಹಾಕಬಹುದು.

ಮಧುಮೇಹ : ಹಾಗಲಕಾಯನ್ನು ಚೆನ್ನಾಗಿ ಬೇಯಿಸಿ ಆ ನೀರನ್ನು ಕುಡಿಯಬೇಕು. ಬೇವಿನ ಸೊಪ್ಪು ಮತ್ತು ಸೀಬೆ ಸೊಪ್ಪು ಎರಡನ್ನು ನೀರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಬೇಯಿಸಿ ಕೊಡುವುದು.ಒಂದು ಸೇರು ನೀರನ್ನು ಹಾಕಿ ಚತುರ್ಭಾಗ ಮಾಡಿ ನೀಡುವುದು.

ಕಾಮಾಲೆ : ಮಜ್ಜಿಗೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ವಲ್ಪ ಕೊತ್ತಂಬರಿ ಪುಡಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಹುಣಸೆ ಚಿಗುರನ್ನು ಅರೆದು ಕುಡಿಯುವುದು.

ರಕ್ತಸ್ರಾವ : ಕೆಂಪು ಉತ್ತರಾಣಿ ಸೊಪ್ಪನ್ನು ಹಾಲಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಬೆರೆಸಿ ಕೊಡಬಹುದು ಅಥವಾ ಸಕ್ಕರೆ ಜೊತೆ ಉಂಡೆ ಮಾಡಿ ಮೂರು ದಿನ ಕೊಟ್ಟರೆ ರಕ್ತಸ್ರಾವ ನಿಂತುಹೋಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಕೆಮ್ಮು : ಶುಂಠಿ, ಮೆಣಸು, ಹಿಪ್ಪಲಿ ಮೂರನ್ನು ಅರೆದು ಸಮತೂಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಜೇನುತುಪ್ಪದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಾಕಿಅವರೇಕಾಳಿನ ಗಾತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾತ್ರ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುವುದು.

ಲಕ್ಷ : ಒಂದು ತೊಲ ಬೆಳ್ಳುಳ್ಳಿಯನ್ನು ಕಾಲು ಲೀಟರ್ ಹಾಲಲ್ಲಿ ಬೆರೆಸಿ ಕುಡಿದರೆ ವಾಸಿಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಹೊಟ್ಟೆನೋವು : ಶೇಂಗ ಲವಣವನ್ನು ಪುಡಿ ಮಾಡಿ ಒಂದು ಅಳತೆ ಬಿಸಿನೀರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಕೊಟ್ಟರೆವಾಸಿಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಚಳಿಜ್ವರಕ್ಕೆ : ನಿಂಬೆಹಣ್ಣಿನಲ್ಲಿ ತುಂಬಿಸೊಪ್ಪಿನ ರಸವನ್ನು ಹಾಕಿ ಒಂದು ಚೂರು ಉಪ್ಪು ಹಾಕಿ ಕೊಟ್ಟರೆನಿಂತು ಹೋಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಆಮಶಂಕೆ : ಗಸಗಸೆಯನ್ನು ಚೆನ್ನಾಗಿ ಅರೆದು ತಣ್ಣಗಿರುವ ಹಾಲಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಕೊಟ್ಟರೆ ನಿಂತು ಹೋಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಹೀಗೆ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನರು ಕಾಯಿಲೆಗೆ ಔಷಧ ನೀಡುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಇವರು ಸಸ್ಯ, ಗಿಡಮೂಲಿಕೆ, ಚಕ್ಕೆ, ಎಲೆಗಳನ್ನು ಬಳಸಿ ಔಷಧಿ ತಯಾರು ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ತಂದೆಯಾದವನು ಮಗನಿಗೆ ಔಷಧಿ ತಯಾರು ಮಾಡುವುದನ್ನು ಹೇಳಿಕೊಡುತ್ತಾನೆ. ಇವರಲ್ಲಿ ವೈದ್ಯ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಆಯುರ್ವೇದವೂ ಜನಪದ ವೈದ್ಯವೂ ಸಮಸಮವಾಗಿ ಬೆರೆತು ಹೋಗಿದೆ.ಗಿಡಮೂಲಿಕೆಗಳಿಂದ ತಯಾರು ಮಾಡಿದ ಗುಳಿಗೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಇವರ ಔಷಧಿ ಪದ್ಧತಿ ಸರಳವಾಗಿ ರೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ಗುಣಪಡಿಸುವ ರೀತಿ ಸಹಜವಾಗಿ ಇದೆ. ಇವರನ್ನು ನಾಟಿ ವೈದ್ಯ ಪಂಡಿತರು ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ.

3) **ಉಪಕಸುಬಾಗಿ ರೇಷ್ಮೆ ನೂಲು ಬಿಚ್ಚುವುದು, ಮಗ್ಗ ನೇಯುವುದು, ಕೃಷಿ ಮತ್ತು ಹೈನುಗಾರಿಕೆ :**

ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಸಮುದಾಯವು ತಮ್ಮ ಜೀವನ ನಿರ್ವಹಣೆಗೆ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಮೂಲವಾಗಿ ರೇಷ್ಮೆ ನೂಲು ಬಿಚ್ಚುವುದು, ಮಗ್ಗ ನೇಯುವುದು, ಕೃಷಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಹೈನುಗಾರಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ತಮ್ಮ ಉಪಕಸುಬಾಗಿ ಇಂದಿಗೂ ಉಳಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಕಾಣುತ್ತೇವೆ. ರೇಷ್ಮೆ ನೂಲು ಬಿಚ್ಚಲು ಮಣ್ಣಿನಿಂದ ಒಲೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕಟ್ಟಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಇದನ್ನು 'ಉಬ್ಬೊಲೆ' ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ.ರೇಷ್ಮೆ ಮಾರುಕಟ್ಟೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ರೇಷ್ಮೆಗೂಡನ್ನು ಖರೀದಿಸಿ ಮನೆಗೆ ತಂದು ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಗಂಟು ಗೂಡುಗಳನ್ನು ಬೇರ್ಪಡಿಸಿ, ನಯವಾದ ರೇಷ್ಮೆಗೂಡುಗಳನ್ನು ಆಯ್ದು ತೂಕವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿ ಬಿದಿರಿನ ತಟ್ಟೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಶೇಖರಿಸಿಡುತ್ತಾರೆ.ನಂತರ ಉಬ್ಬೊಲೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಬಾನಿಯನ್ನಿರಿಸಿ ಭತ್ತದ ಹೊಟ್ಟನ್ನು ಒಲೆಯ ಬಾಯಿಗೆ ಹಾಕಿ ಬೆಂಕಿ ಹಚ್ಚುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಬಾನಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಬಿಸಿ ನೀರನ್ನು ಕಾಯಿಸಿ ಅದರ ಮೇಲೆ ಅಡ್ಡ ಪಟ್ಟಿಗಳನ್ನಿಟ್ಟು ರೇಷ್ಮೆಗೂಡನ್ನು

ಉಬ್ಬಿಕಾಯಿಸುವ ಬಿದಿರಿನ ಬುಟ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ತುಂಬಿ ಗೂಡಿನ ಮೇಲೆ ಗೋಣಿಚೀಲ ಹೊದಿಸಿ ಬಾನಿಯ ಮೇಲಿಟ್ಟು ಬಿಸಿ ನೀರಿನ ಹಬೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಗೂಡನ್ನು ಕಾಯಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಇದನ್ನು 'ಉಬ್ಬಿ ಕಾಯಿಸುವುದು' ಎಂದು ಹೇಳುತ್ತಾರೆ.ರೇಷ್ಮೆಗೂಡನ್ನು ಉಬ್ಬಿ ಕಾಯಿಸಿದ ನಂತರ ಗಾಳಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹಾರಲು ಬಿಡುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಇದು ರೇಷ್ಮೆಗೂಡಿನಿಂದ ನೂಲನ್ನು ಬಿಚ್ಚುವ ಪ್ರಥಮ ಹಂತವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ.ಮಾರನೆಯ ದಿನ ಉಬ್ಬಿ ಕಾಯಿಸಿದ ಗೂಡನ್ನು ಸರಿಯಾದ ಪ್ರಮಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ತೂಕ ಮಾಡಿ ಕೆಲಸಗಾರರಿಗೆ ನೀಡುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಅವರು ಗೂಡನ್ನು ಕುದಿಯುವ ಬಿಸಿನೀರಲ್ಲಿ ಹಾಕಿ ರೇಷ್ಮೆ ನೂಲಿನ ಎಳೆಯನ್ನು ಬಿಡಿಸಿ ರಾಟೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಪೋಣಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ರೇಷ್ಮೆಗೂಡಿನಿಂದ ನೂಲನ್ನು ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ ಬೇರ್ಪಡಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.ನಂತರ ಅರ್ಧಂಬರ್ಧ ಬೆಂದು ಗೂಡಿನೊಳಗಿರುವ ರೇಷ್ಮೆಹುಳುವನ್ನು ಬಿಸಿ ನೀರಿನಿಂದ ತೆಗೆದು ತೊಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಹಾಕುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಇದನ್ನು 'ಗೊಳ್ಳೆ' ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಇದರ ನಾರನ್ನು 'ನಟ್ಟಿ' ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಇದನ್ನು ಬಿಸಿಲಲ್ಲಿ ಒಣಗಿಸಿಶೇಖರಿಸಿಡುತ್ತಾರೆ.ಹೀಗೆ ರೇಷ್ಮೆನೂಲು, ಗೊಳ್ಳೆ ಮತ್ತು ನಟ್ಟಿಯನ್ನು ಮಾರಾಟ ಮಾಡಿ ಬಂದ ಹಣದಲ್ಲಿ ತಮ್ಮ ಬದುಕನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ.ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿಯೇ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಸಮುದಾಯದವರನ್ನು 'ಮಗ್ಗದವರು' ಎಂದು ನೆರಹೊರೆಯ ಸಮುದಾಯದವರು ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ.ರೇಷ್ಮೆ ತಯಾರಿಕೆ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಕೃಷಿ ಮತ್ತು ಹೈನುಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಅವಲಂಬಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅಲ್ಲ ಪ್ರಮಾಣದ ಕೃಷಿ ಜಮೀನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವವರು ಭತ್ತ, ರಾಗಿ, ಜೋಳ, ಕಬ್ಬು, ಹಾಗೂ ದ್ವಿದಳ ಧಾನ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಯುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ.ಜಮೀನು ರಹಿತ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಜನರು ಕುರಿ, ಕೋಳಿ,ದನ, ಹಸು-ಕರುಗಳನ್ನು ಸಾಕುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಹೈನುಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಜೀವನದ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ

ಉಪಸಂಹಾರ:

ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ದಿನಮಾನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಬದಲಾಗುತ್ತಿರುವ ಜಾಗತೀಕರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಆಧುನಿಕತೆಯ ಪ್ರಭಾವವು ಜನಪದದ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಬದುಕಿನ ಮೇಲೆ ತೀಕ್ಷ್ಣವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುತ್ತಿದೆಯಾದರೂ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನಾಂಗಕ್ಕೆ ವಂಶದಿಂದ ವಂಶಕ್ಕೆ; ಹಿರಿತಲೆಯಿಂದ ಕಿರಿತಲೆಗೆ ಬಳುವಳಿಯಾಗಿ ಬಂದಿರುವ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಕುಲಕಸುಬುಗಳನ್ನು ಜೀವನಾಡಿಯಂತೆ ಉಳಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಬದುಕುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಆಶ್ಚರ್ಯಚಕಿತವಾಗಿದೆ. ಬದುಕಿಸುದ್ದಕ್ಕೂ ನಡೆಯುವ ನಡಿಗೆಯ ನೆರಳಿನಂತೆ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಮೈಗೂಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಜನಾಂಗವಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಯೂರಿರುವ ಜನಸಾಮಾನ್ಯರಿಗೆ ಕಣಿಯನ್ ಜನಾಂಗದ ಇರುವಿಕೆಯ ಪರಿವೇ ಇಲ್ಲದಿರುವುದು ಭವಿಷ್ಯದ ಬೆಳಕಲ್ಲಿ ಕತ್ತಲು ಕವಿದಂತಾಗಿರುವುದು ಸತ್ಯವೆನಿಸಿ...! ಆಧುನಿಕತೆಯ ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳ ಕುಲಕಸುಬುಗಳು ಅವುಗಳ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಸಾರುವ ಅಂಶವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ.ಆದರೆ ಶರವೇಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಜನ ಜೀವನವನ್ನು ಆವರಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿರುವ ಆಧುನಿಕತೆಯೂ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟುಗಳ ಜೀವಾಂಶವಾಗಿರುವ ಕುಲಕಸುಬುಗಳನ್ನು ಅವಸಾನದ ಅಂಚಿಗೆ ದೂಡುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಕಣಿಗೆ ಕಾಣುವ ಸತ್ಯಾಂಶವಾಗಿ ನಿಲ್ಲುತ್ತದೆ.ಕುಲಕಸುಬುಗಳು ವಿನಾಶದ ಅಂಚಿನಲ್ಲಿವೆ. ಇದನ್ನು ಉಳಿಸಿ-ಬೆಳೆಸಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂಬ ಮಾತು ಎಲ್ಲೆಡೆ ಕೇಳಿ ಬರುತ್ತಿದೆ.ಆದರೆ ಈ ಕುಲಕಸುಬುಗಳು ನಶಿಸಿ ಹೋಗುತ್ತಿರುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣಗಳೇನು?ಈ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳು ಎಂತಹ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತಿವೆ?ತಮ್ಮಲ್ಲಿರುವ ವೃತ್ತಿ ಪರಿಣಿತಿಯನ್ನು ತೊರೆದು ಮತ್ಯಾವ ಹೊಸ ಕೆಲಸಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ತೊಡಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿವೆ?ಎಂಬುದರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳು ನಡೆಯಬೇಕಾಗಿರುವುದು ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಸಮಾಜದ ಪರಿವರ್ತನೆಯ ಪ್ರವಾಹಕ್ಕೆ ಈ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಆಸೆ-ಆಕಾಂಕ್ಷೆಗಳು ಒಪ್ಪಬಹುದು, ಇಲ್ಲವೇ ಪೂರಕವಾಗಿರಬಹುದು.ಆದರೆ ಆಧುನಿಕ ಸಮಾಜದ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಯಾವುದೇ ಸಂಬಂಧ ಬೆಳೆಸಿಲ್ಲದ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟುಗಳು ಹಳೆಯ ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೊಂದಿಕೊಳ್ಳದೆ, ನೂತನ ಆವಿಷ್ಕಾರಗಳಿಗೂ ಹೊಂದಿಕೊಳ್ಳದೆ ಅತಂತ್ರ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಯಲ್ಲಿದ್ದಾರೆ.ಈ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳ ಜನರು ಆಧುನಿಕತೆಯ ಜನರ ಅನುಕರಣೆಯಿಂದತಮ್ಮ ಮೂಲ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ, ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯ, ಆಚಾರ-ವಿಚಾರದ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಅನ್ಯ ವರ್ಗದ ಜನರ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ.ಆಧುನಿಕತೆಯ ಆಗುಹೋಗು ಇವರ ಜೀವನದ ಮೇಲೆ ಸಕಾರಾತ್ಮಕವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ನಕಾರಾತ್ಮಕವಾಗಿ ಪರಿಣಾಮವನ್ನು ಬೀರುತ್ತಿದೆ.ಇವರ ಕುಲಕಸುಬುಗಳನ್ನು ಆಧುನಿಕ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಆರ್ಥಿಕವಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ವಿಫಲವಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ್ಯ, ಮಾಟ-ಮಂತ್ರ, ನಾಟ ವೈದ್ಯ ಪದ್ಧತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಜನರು ನಂಬುವಂತಹ ಮನಸ್ಥಿತಿ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಯಾಗಿರುವುದು ಒಂದು ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿ ಕಣ್ಮಂದೆ ನಿಲ್ಲುತ್ತದೆ.ಆಧುನಿಕತೆಯು ಕುಲಕಸುಬುಗಳನ್ನು ಮರೆಮಾಚಿ ಜೀವನವನ್ನು ಅರಸಿ ಪಟ್ಟಣಗಳಿಗೆ ವಲಸೆ ಹೋಗಿ ಕೂಲಿ ಕೆಲಸಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿ ತಮ್ಮ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಮೂಲವನ್ನೆ ಮರೆಸುವಂತಾಗುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ತೊಚ್ಚಿನೀಯವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಟಿಪ್ಪಣಿಗಳು

ರೀನಾ.ಟಿ.ಬಿ. (2016), ಕುಲ ಕಸುಬು ಮತ್ತು ಜನ ಬದುಕು-ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯ ಅಕಾಡೆಮಿ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು.

ಡಾ. ಮಧು ಗುಂಡ್ಲುಪೇಟೆ, (2017), ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟುಗಳ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ, ಪ್ರಜಾ ವಿಕಾಸ ಸೇವಾ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆ, ಹೆಬ್ಬಾಳು, ಮೈಸೂರು

ಡಾ. ಕೆ. ಎಂ. ಮೈತ್ರಿ, ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಕುಲಕಸುಬುಗಳು, ಪ್ರಸಾರಾಂಗ, ಕನ್ನಡ ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾನಿಲಯ, ಹಂಪಿ,

ಡಾ. ಆರ್.ರಾಮಕೃಷ್ಣ(2002) - ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟುಗಳು - ಪ್ರಸಾರಾಂಗ, ಮಾನಸ ಗಂಗೋತ್ರಿ, ಮೈಸೂರು

ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯ ಒಂದು ಅವಲೋಕನ

(On overview of the functioning of the judiciary in India at present)

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ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾವನೆ : (Abstract)

ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಭಾರತದ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯ ಒಂದು ಅವಲೋಕನ ಶುಭಾ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾದದ್ದು ಎಂದರೆ ತಪ್ಪಾಗಲಾರದು. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಸಂದರ್ಭ/ಕಾಲಘಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗವೂ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಒಂದು ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ಅಂಗವಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಇದು ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಸಂರಕ್ಷಣೆಯ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಾನತೆಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುವ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಇದರ ಕಾರ್ಯ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತದಲ್ಲಿ ಅತ್ಯಾವಶ್ಯಕ ಎನ್ನಬಹುದು. ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಬಂದು 75 ವರ್ಷಗಳು ಕಳೆದರೂ ಕೂಡ ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ಇನ್ನೂ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸಮತೋಲನ, ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮತೋಲನ, ನಿರುದ್ಯೋಗ, ಬಡತನ, ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬರಿಗೂ ಕೈಗೆಟುಕದಂತಹ ಉನ್ನತ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ, ಸಂವಿಧಾನಾತ್ಮಕ ನ್ಯಾಯ ಸಿಗದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆ ಶುಭಾ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಅಷ್ಟೇ ಅಲ್ಲದೇ ಮೇಲಿನ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಶಾಶ್ವತ ಪರಿಹಾರ ಕಲ್ಪಿಸುವ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಸಾಧನ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗವೇ ಆಗಿದೆ.

Introduction to Judicial Activism : (ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಯ ಪರಿಚಯ)

ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಅಥವಾ ಶಾಸನಗಳ ನೂತನ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಕಾನೂನನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ನ್ಯಾಯವನ್ನು ಖಾತ್ರಿಪಡಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಧೀಶರು ವಹಿಸುವ ಪೂರ್ವಭಾವಿ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯು ಸೂಚಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಇಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆ ಎಂಬುದು ನ್ಯಾಯಾಧೀಶರ ಕ್ರಿಯೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ನಿಂತಿದೆ. ಅಂದರೆ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಧೀಶರು ತಮ್ಮ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿಯ ಯಾವುದೇ ಪ್ರಕರಣಗಳನ್ನಾಗಲಿ ಸಾಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ ಚೌಕಟ್ಟಿನೊಳಗೆ ಕಟ್ಟಿಕೊಡುವಂತಹ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗೆ ನ್ಯಾಯಿಕ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆ ಎನ್ನುತ್ತೇವೆ.

ಆದರೆ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗವು ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಯಾವುದೇ ಅಂಗಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗಿಯಾಗದೆ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರವಾಗಿ ಸಾಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ ನೆಲೆಗಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ತೀರ್ಪು ನೀಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಜನರಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಮರಸ್ಯವನ್ನು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯತೆಯ ಮನಸ್ಥಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಕಟ್ಟಿಕೊಡುವ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನ ಹಿಂದೆಂದಿಗಿಂತಲೂ ಇಂದು ಶುಭಾ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ ಎನ್ನಬಹುದು. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ, ಇಂದು ನಮ್ಮನ್ನು ಆಳುವ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಧರ್ಮಾಧಾರಿತ ರಾಜಕೀಯಕ್ಕೆ ಅಂಟಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿರುವ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಇಂತಹ ಪ್ರಕರಣಗಳನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ಭೇದಿಸಬೇಕು. ಜನರಲ್ಲಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕತೆಗಿಂತ ಧರ್ಮತೀತವಾಗಿ ಹೇಗೆ ಒಬ್ಬರಿಗೊಬ್ಬರು ಪರಸ್ಪರ ಹೊಂದಿಕೊಂಡು ಜೀವಿಸಬೇಕು ಎಂಬುದಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಪಟ್ಟ ಹಾಗೆ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಲಯಗಳು ತೀರ್ಪು ನೀಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಗೆ ಆದ್ಯತೆ ನೀಡಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

Meaning and Definitions of Judicial Activism:

(ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯ ಅರ್ಥ ಮತ್ತು ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಗಳು)

Meaning (ಅರ್ಥ) : ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯ ಅರ್ಥವನ್ನು ನಾಗರಿಕರ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳನ್ನು ರಕ್ಷಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ನ್ಯಾಯವನ್ನು ಖಾತ್ರಿಪಡಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಪೂರ್ವಭಾವಿ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆ / ಕ್ರಿಯಾಚಟುವಟಿಕೆ ಎನ್ನುತ್ತೇವೆ.

ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯು 1947ರಲ್ಲಿ United States ನಲ್ಲಿ ಹೊರಹೊಮ್ಮಿತು. ನಂತರ 1970ರ ದಶಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತದ ಪ್ರಭಾವಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಧೀಶರುಗಳು ಈ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯನ್ನು ನಮ್ಮ ಸಾರ್ವಭೌಮ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಗಣರಾಜ್ಯದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಗೆ ಪೂರಕವಾಗುವಂತೆ ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡರು. ಈ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯು

ನಮ್ಮ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಧೀಶರುಗಳಿಗೆ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳನ್ನು ಸರಳವಾಗಿ ಅರ್ಥೈಸಲು ಅಧಿಕಾರ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗ ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯಾಂಗಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಎತ್ತಿ ಹಿಡಿಯಲು ವಿಫಲವಾದಾಗ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾವಾದವು / ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯು ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗ ಹಾಗೂ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಂಗಗಳ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಇದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ

ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಕಾಪಾಡಲು ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಸದಾ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲವಾಗಿರುವಲ್ಲಿ ಇದರ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ (ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆ) ತುಂಬಾ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಕಾರಿಯಾದದ್ದು. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಸಂದರ್ಭಕ್ಕೆ.

Definitions of Judicial Activism : (ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಗಳು)

- **ಆಕ್ಸಫರ್ಡ್ ನಿಘಂಟಿನ ಪ್ರಕಾರ :** ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯು ಕಾನೂನುಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಅನೀತಿ ಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಅಸಂವಿಧಾನಿಕವೆಂದು ಘೋಷಿಸಲು ನ್ಯಾಯಾಧೀಶರುಗಳಿರುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಬಹುದು.
- **ಮೆರಿಯಮ್-ವೆಬ್‌ಸ್ಟರ್ ನಿಘಂಟಿನ ಪ್ರಕಾರ :** ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯವನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸಲು ಕಾನೂನನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಧೀಶರು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಸಕ್ರಿಯ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸಲು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುವ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ತತ್ವಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳುತ್ತದೆ.
- **ಕರಿಯರ ಕಾನೂನು ನಿಘಂಟು :** ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳನ್ನು ಸರಳವಾಗಿ ಅನ್ವಯಿಸುವ ಬದಲು ಕಾನೂನನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಧೀಶರು ಸಕ್ರಿಯ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸುವ ಅಭ್ಯಾಸ.
- ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆ ಅಥವಾ ಕ್ರಿಯಾವಾದದ ಪಿತಾಮಹರಾದ ನ್ಯಾಯಮೂರ್ತಿ ಪಿ.ಎನ್. ಭಗವತಿ ರವರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ “ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾವಾದವು ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಸಾಹಸವಲ್ಲ, ಇದು ಕಾನೂನುಗಳ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಕ್ಕೆ ಕ್ರಿಯಾತ್ಮಕ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಗತಿಶೀಲ ವಿಧಾನವಾಗಿದೆ. ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗವು ಜನರ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳ ರಕ್ಷಕನಾಗಿ ತನ್ನ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಂಗ ಹಾಗೂ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗದ ಮಿತಿ ಮೀರಿದವುಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸುತ್ತದೆ”. ನ್ಯಾಯಮೂರ್ತಿ ಭಗವತಿ ರವರ ಮಹತ್ವದ ತೀರ್ಪುಗಳು ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಗೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗಳಾಗಿವೆ. ಉದಾ:-
- **ಮೇನಕಾಂಗಾಧಿ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಯೂನಿಯನ್ ಆಫ್ ಇಂಡಿಯಾ (1978) :** ಇದರಲ್ಲಿ ಜೀವನ ಮತ್ತು ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯದ ಹಕ್ಕನ್ನು ವಿಸ್ತರಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಇಂತಹ ತೀರ್ಪುಗಳು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದಿಂದ ಹೊರಬರಬೇಕಾದ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯತೆ ಇದೆ.

Role of Judicial Activism in India at present : (ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯ ಪಾತ್ರ)

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸುಪ್ರೀಂಕೋರ್ಟ್ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಹೈಕೋರ್ಟ್‌ಗಳು ಯಾವುದೇ ಕಾನೂನಿನ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಿಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿವೆ. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ, ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯು ನಾಗರಿಕರ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳನ್ನು ರಕ್ಷಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಪೂರ್ವಭಾವಿ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ಸೂಚಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧೀನ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಲಯಗಳು ಕಾನೂನುಗಳ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಿಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಬೇಕು.

ಇಂತಹ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾವಾದವನ್ನು ಮೊದಲಬಾರಿಗೆ 1947ರಲ್ಲಿ ಅಮೇರಿಕಾದ ಇತಿಹಾಸಕಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಶಿಕ್ಷಣತಜ್ಞ ಅರ್ಥರ್ ಷೆಸಿಂಗರ್ ಜೂನಿಯರ್ ರಚಿಸಿದರು. ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಪೂರಕವಾಗಿ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾವಾದದ ಅಡಿಪಾಯವನ್ನು ಪಿ.ಎನ್.ಭಗವತಿ, ವಿ.ಆರ್.ಕೃಷ್ಣ ಅಯ್ಯರ್, ಚಿನ್ನಪ್ಪರೆಡ್ಡಿ, ಡಿ.ಎ.ದೇಸಾಯಿ ರವರು ಹಾಕಿದರು.

ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯು ತುಂಬಾ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯವಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಇದರಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಪಾತ್ರ ಏನು? ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸೋಣ.

- 1) ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಇತರ ಅಂಗಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯಾಪಕ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರ. ಇದನ್ನು ಹತ್ತಿಕ್ಕಲು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿದೆ.
- 2) ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ತತ್ವಗಳು ನಿರಂತರವಾಗಿ ಅನವತಿ ಹಾದಿ ಹಿಡಿಯುತ್ತಿರುವುದು. ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಬಂದು 75 ವರ್ಷಗಳೇ ಸಂದಿದ್ದರೂ, ಇನ್ನೂ ಕೆಲವು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಸ್ಥಳಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಾನತೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಸಿಗದಿರುವುದು.
- 3) ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಗೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ತುರ್ತಾಗಿ ಸ್ಪಂದಿಸದಿರುವುದು.
- 4) ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ದೇಶದ ದೀರ್ಘಕಾಲೀನ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಪರಿಹಾರ ಕಂಡುಕೊಳ್ಳದೇ ಇರುವುದು ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗವು ತನ್ನ ಕ್ರಿಯಾವಾದದ ಮೂಲಕ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳಿಗೆ ಎಚ್ಚರಿಕೆ ಕೊಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಪರಿಹಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಸ್ಪಂದಿಸುವ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡಬೇಕಿರುವುದು. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತದಲ್ಲಿ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯ.
- 5) ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಸನ್ನಿವೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತ್ಯಾತೀತ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಾಜವಾದಿ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಅಪಾಯದ ಮುನ್ನೂಚನೆಗಳು ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತಿದ್ದು, ಇವುಗಳ ಸಂರಕ್ಷಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯ ಪಾತ್ರ ಅತಿ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾದದ್ದು.

Recent examples of Judicial Activism in India :

(ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯ ಇತ್ತೀಚಿನ ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗಳು)

ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಸಂದರ್ಭದ ಕಾಲಘಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಸುಪ್ರೀಂ ಕೋರ್ಟ್ ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ನಡುವೆ ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ವಿವಾದಗಳು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಯಾಗುತ್ತಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಬಹುದು. ಇತ್ತೀಚೆಗೆ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗ ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯಾಂಗದ ಮೇಲೆ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಮಧ್ಯೆ ಪ್ರವೇಶ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗ ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯಾಂಗಕ್ಕೆ ತನ್ನ ಕೆಲಸ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾರ್ವಭೌಮತೆಯನ್ನು ಕಂಡುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂಬ ಮಾತುಗಳು ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗದ ವಲಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಕೇಳಿಬರುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಇತ್ತೀಚೆಗೆ ;

ಹಣಕಾಸು ಸಚಿವ ಅರುಣ್‌ಜೇಟ್ಟಿ ರವರು ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಅತಿಕ್ರಮಣದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ತಮ್ಮ ಕಳವಳವನ್ನು ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅದು ಏನೆಂದರೆ “ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗವು ತನ್ನದೇ ಆದ ‘ಲಕ್ಷ್ಮಣರೇಖೆ’ಯನ್ನು ಸೆಳೆಯಬೇಕು ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯಾಂಗದ ಡೋಮನ್ ಅನ್ನು ಅತಿಕ್ರಮಿಸುವ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಬಾರದು” ಎಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

- ಇತ್ತೀಚೆಗೆ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತಿರುವ ಬರವನ್ನು ನಿಭಾಯಿಸಲು ಹೊಸ ನೀತಿಯನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಲು ಸುಪ್ರೀಂಕೋರ್ಟ್ ಕೇಂದ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ಆದೇಶಿಸಿದೆ.
- ಇತ್ತೀಚೆಗೆ ನೌಕಾಪಡೆಯಲ್ಲಿ (ನೌಕಾಪಡೆಯ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ) ಪತ್ನಿ ವಿನಿಮಯದ ಆರೋಪಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಲು ವಿಶೇಷ ಹಾಗೂ ತನಿಖಾ ತಂಡವನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಿದೆ. ಇನ್ನೂ
- ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಡ್ಯಾನ್ಸ್ ಬಾರ್‌ಗಳಿಗೆ 2 ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪರವಾನಗಿ ನೀಡಬೇಕೆಂದು ಅದು ಬಯಸಿದೆ. ಇವೆಲ್ಲಾ ಅಂಶಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ ಸುಪ್ರೀಂಕೋರ್ಟ್‌ನ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗ ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯಾಂಗಗಳು ಪ್ರಶ್ನಿಸುತ್ತಿವೆ.

ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಪಟ್ಟಂತೆ ಸುಪ್ರೀಂಕೋರ್ಟ್ ಸರ್ಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ನೀಡಿರುವ ಆದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲವೊಂದು ಪ್ರಕರಣಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯನ್ನು ನಾವು ಕಾಣಬಹುದು.

1) ಬರ ನಿರ್ವಹಣೆಗೆ ಹೊಸ ನೀತಿ ರೂಪಿಸಲು ಕೇಂದ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ಸುಪ್ರೀಂ ಆದೇಶ :

ಇತ್ತೀಚಿನ ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಇತರ ಕೆಲವು ಸ್ಥಳಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ರೈತರ ಆತ್ಮಹತ್ಯೆಗಳು ಹೆಚ್ಚುತ್ತಿರುವ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸುಪ್ರೀಂ ಕೋರ್ಟ್ ಕಳವಳ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸಿ, ಇಂತಹ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೊಸ ನೀತಿ ರಚಿಸುವಂತೆ ಕೇಂದ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ಆದೇಶಿಸಿರುವುದು ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಗೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ಉದಾಹರಣೆ.

2) ಸುಸ್ತಿ ಸಾಲ ಸಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಲು ಸರ್ಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಸುಪ್ರೀಂ ಆದೇಶ :

ಇತ್ತೀಚೆಗೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ವಲಯದ ಬ್ಯಾಂಕ್‌ಗಳಿಂದ ಬಾರಿ ಪ್ರಮಾಣದ ವಂಚನೆಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಲು ಸಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ನೇಮಿಸುವಂತೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಆದೇಶಿಸಿದೆ. ಇದೂ ಕೂಡ ನ್ಯಾಯಿಕ ಕ್ರಿಯಾವಾದಕ್ಕೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ಉದಾಹರಣೆ.

3) ಭಾರತೀಯ ಕ್ರಿಕೆಟ್ ನಿಯಂತ್ರಣಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಸುಧಾರಣಾ ಮಂಡಳಿ (BCCI) ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸುವ ವಿಚಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಸುಪ್ರೀಂ ಕೋರ್ಟ್ ಅತ್ಯುತ್ತಮ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ;

BCCI ಖಾಸಗಿ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಯಾಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಇದನ್ನು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರಣಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಮುಂದಾಗುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಒಳ್ಳೆಯ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆ ಮತ್ತು ಇದು ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಗೆ ಒಂದು ಪೂರಕ ಹೆಜ್ಜೆ ಎನ್ನಬಹುದು.

What should be the Judicial System in present day Democratic India :

(ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಹೇಗಿರಬೇಕು)

ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯು ಇದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಶ್ರಮಿಸಬೇಕು.

- 1) ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ : ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಂಗ ಮತ್ತು ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗದ ಪ್ರಭಾವದಿಂದ ಮುಕ್ತ.
- 2) ನಿಷ್ಪಕ್ಷಪಾತತೆ : ನಿಷ್ಪಕ್ಷಪಾತ ಮತ್ತು ತಟಸ್ಥ ನಿರ್ಧಾರ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲವಾಗಬೇಕು.
- 3) ಪ್ರವೇಶಿಸುವಿಕೆ : ಎಲ್ಲಾ ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ನ್ಯಾಯಿಕ ಸುಲಭ ಪ್ರವೇಶಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಮುಂದಾಗಬೇಕು.
- 4) ದಕ್ಷತೆ : ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಅನೇಕ ಪ್ರಕರಣಗಳು ಸಾಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ ನೆಲೆಗಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಹರಿಸುವ ದಕ್ಷತೆ ಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ.
- 5) ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆ : ಮುಕ್ತ ಮತ್ತು ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯುತ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುವ ಇದರ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆ ಇದೆ.
- 6) ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆ : ನ್ಯಾಯಾಧೀಶರುಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳಿಗೆ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯಾಗಿರುವುದು ಕೂಡ ನ್ಯಾಯಿಕ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಗೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ಉದಾಹರಣೆ ಎನ್ನಬಹುದು.
- 7) ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ವಿಶ್ವಾಸವನ್ನು ಗಳಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಮುಂದಾಗಬೇಕಿದೆ. ಹಾಗೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅನೀತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಶ್ನಿಸುವ ಮತ್ತು ಶಿಕ್ಷಿಸುವ ವಿಚಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಇನ್ನೂ ವಿಶ್ವಾಸನೀಯ ಆಗಬೇಕಿದೆ.

Conclusion : (ಉಪಸಂಹಾರ)

ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಭಾರತದ ಸಂದರ್ಭಕ್ಕೆ ಒಂದು ಉತ್ತಮ ಕ್ರಿಯೆ ಆಗಿದ್ದು, ಇದರ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಒಂದುವೇಳೆ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲವಾಗದೇ ಹೋದರೆ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಭಾರತದ ರಕ್ಷಣೆ ಕಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ರಕ್ಷಕನಾಗಿ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯಶೀಲವಾಗಿದ್ದರೂ ಕೂಡ ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ಅನೇಕ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ, ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಒಂದುವೇಳೆ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ನಿಷ್ಕ್ರಿಯವಾದರೆ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಅಳಿವು ಆದಂತೆ, ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಉಳಿವು ಮತ್ತು ಒಕ್ಕೂಟ ಭಾರತವನ್ನು ಸಂರಕ್ಷಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗಕ್ಕೆ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾವಾದ / ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯ ಎಂದೆನ್ನಬಹುದು.

Resources : (ಆಕರಗ್ರಂಥಗಳು)

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ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ವ್ಯಾಪಾರಕ್ಕಿಂದು ಬಂದ ಐರೋಪ್ಯ ಕ್ರಮೇಣ ಆಡಳಿತದ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಹಿಡಿದು ಆಡಳಿತ ನಡೆಸಿದರು.ನಂತರ, ಕ್ರಮೇಣವಾಗಿ ಭಾರತೀಯರಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯತೆಯ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯ ಉಗಮದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಭಾರತದ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಹೋರಾಟವು ಪ್ರಾರಂಭವಾಯಿತು.ಇದರ ಫಲವಾಗಿ 1947 ಆಗಸ್ಟ್ 15 ರಂದು ಭಾರತವು ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರವಾಯಿತು. ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ಭಾರತದ ಆಡಳಿತಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಮನಗಂಡು ನಮ್ಮ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಹೋರಾಟಗಾರರು ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ರಚನಾ ಸಭೆಯನ್ನು 1946ರಲ್ಲಿ ರಚಿಸಿದರು, ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ರಚನಾ ಸಭೆಯು ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ಸೂಕ್ತವಾದ ಸಂವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಿ 1949 ನವೆಂಬರ್ 26 ರಂದು ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿತು, ನಮ್ಮ ಸಂವಿಧಾನವು ದಿನಾಂಕ:26 ಜನವರಿ 1950 ರಂದು ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಬರುವುದರೊಂದಿಗೆ ಭಾರತವು ಗಣರಾಜ್ಯ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾಗಿ ವಿಶ್ವದಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ದೊಡ್ಡ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಎಂಬ ಹೆಗ್ಗಳಿಕೆಗೆ ಪಾತ್ರವಾಯಿತು. ಈ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತವು ಒಂದು ಸಂಯುಕ್ತ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಎಂದು ಘೋಷಿಸಿದ್ದರು.ಭಾರತವು 1950 ಜನವರಿ 26 ರಿಂದ ತನ್ನ ದೇಶದ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಯುಕ್ತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಈ ಸಂಯುಕ್ತ ಮಾದರಿ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಆಡಳಿತವನ್ನು “ಸಹಕಾರಿ ಸಂಯುಕ್ತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ” ನಿಯೋಗಗಳ ಮುಖಾಂತರ ನಡೆಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಬರುತ್ತಿದೆ.“ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಹೋರಾಟ ಮತ್ತು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಏಕೀಕರಣ”, ಇವು ಕನ್ನಡಿಗರ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಭವಿಸಿದ ಎರಡು ಮಹತ್ವದ ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳು.ಇವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತದ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯಗಳಿಸುವುದು ಒಂದು ಮಹತ್ವದ ವಿಷಯವಾದರೆ, ಭಾಷಾವಾರು ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯಗಳ ವಿಂಗಡಣೆಯು ಮತ್ತೊಂದು ಕಠಿಣ ಸವಾಲಾಗಿತ್ತು.ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯನಂತರ ಭಾಷಾವಾರು ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯಗಳ ರಚನೆಯ ಕೂಗು ಕೇಳಿ ಬಂದಿತು.1953 ರಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಹರೂರವರ ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಭಾಷೆಯ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ವಿಂಗಡಣೆ ಮಾಡಲು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಿದರು.ಕನ್ನಡವನ್ನು ಮಾತನಾಡುವಂತಹ ವಿವಿಧ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು, ವಿವಿಧ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹರಿದು ಹಂಚಿಹೋಗಿತ್ತು.ಕನ್ನಡವನ್ನು ಮಾತನಾಡುವ ಜನರನ್ನು ಒಂದುಗೂಡಿಸಿ ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯವನ್ನು ರಚನೆ ಮಾಡುವುದರ ಮೂಲಕ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಏಕೀಕರಣವನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯದ ರಚನೆಯ ನಂತರದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಕನ್ನಡ ಭಾಷೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾತನಾಡುವಂತಹ ಜನರು ವಾಸಿಸುವಂತಹ ಹಲವಾರು ಭೂ ಭಾಗಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಇತರೆ ನೆರೆಯ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹರಿದು ಹಂಚಿಹೋಗಿವೆ. ಇದರ ನಡುವೆಯೇ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವು ತನ್ನ ಸುತ್ತಮುತ್ತಲಿನ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ, ತನ್ನ ಗಡಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಹಲವಾರು ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಈ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ಇತ್ಯರ್ಥಪಡಿಸಲು ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸು ನೀಡುವಂತೆ ನ್ಯಾಯಮೂರ್ತಿ ಮಹರ್ಶಿಚಂದ್ ಮಹಾಜನ್ ರವರ ಅಧ್ಯಕ್ಷತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಾಜನ್ ಆಯೋಗವನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಿತು.

✚ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡಣಾ ಆಯೋಗ

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಷೆಯ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಆಂಧ್ರಪ್ರದೇಶ ರಾಜ್ಯವು ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಬಂದ ಸ್ಫೂರ್ತಿಯಿಂದ ಇತರೆ ಭಾಷಿಕರೂ ಸಹ ತಮ್ಮ ತಮ್ಮ ಭಾಷೆಯ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಭಾಷಾವಾರು ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ರಚನೆ ಮಾಡಬೇಕೆಂದು ಹೋರಾಟವನ್ನು ತೀವ್ರಗೊಳಿಸಿದರು. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡಣಾಆಯೋಗವನ್ನು ನೇಮಿಸಿದರು.ಭಾಷೆಗಳ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡಣೆ ಕುರಿತು ವರದಿ ಮಾಡುವುದು ಈ ಆಯೋಗದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಕಾರ್ಯವಾಗಿತ್ತು.ಫೆಬ್ರವರಿ 1953ರಲ್ಲಿ ಇವರು ಈ ಆಯೋಗದ ಅಧ್ಯಕ್ಷರಾಗಿದ್ದರು. ಕೆ.ಎಂ.ಪಣಿಕ್ಕರ್ ಮತ್ತು ಎಚ್.ಎನ್.ಕುಂಜು ರವರು ಆಯೋಗದ ಇತರೆ ಸದಸ್ಯರಾಗಿದ್ದರು. ಇದನ್ನು ಫೆಬ್ರವರಿ 1953ರಲ್ಲಿ ಆಯೋಗ ಎಂತಲೂ ಸಹ ಕರೆಯುವರು.ಈ ಆಯೋಗವು 38,000 ಮೈಲಿಗಳ ಪ್ರಯಾಣ ಮಾಡಿ, 10,000 ಜನರನ್ನು ಸಂದರ್ಶಿಸಿ 15,225 ನಿವೇದನೆಯ ಪತ್ರಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಿ, ಕೊನೆಗೆ 262 ಪುಟಗಳ ವರದಿಯನ್ನು ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ 30 ಸೆಪ್ಟೆಂಬರ್ 1955 ರಂದು ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿತು.

❖ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿನ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳು

ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಪುನರ್ವಿಂಗಡಣಾ ಆಯೋಗದ ವರದಿಯ ಅನ್ವಯ ಸಂಸತ್ತಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರವು 1956ರಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡಣಾ ಕಾಯಿದೆಯನ್ನು ಅಂಗೀಕರಿಸಿ, ಭಾರತದ ಒಕ್ಕೂಟವನ್ನು ಭಾಷೆಯ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಒಟ್ಟು 14 ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು 6 ಕೇಂದ್ರಾಡಳಿತ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳನ್ನಾಗಿ ವಿಂಗಡಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಕನ್ನಡ ಭಾಷೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾತನಾಡುವ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ಒಟ್ಟುಗೂಡಿಸಿ ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಎಂದು ರಚಿಸಿದರು. ಭಾಷಾವಾರು ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯಗಳು ರಚನೆಯಾದ ನಂತರ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಲವಾರು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ಅಂತರರಾಜ್ಯ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳು ಉದ್ಭವವಾದವು. ನಮ್ಮ ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯವು ಕನ್ನಡಭಾಷೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾತನಾಡುವ ಹಲವಾರು ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ನೆರೆಯ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸೇರಿಕೊಂಡಿವೆ. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವು ತನ್ನ ನೆರೆಯ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಾದ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ, ಕೇರಳ ರಾಜ್ಯದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಕಾಸರಗೋಡನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಂತೆ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಸುತ್ತಮುತ್ತಲಿನ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು, ಆಂಧ್ರಪ್ರದೇಶ ರಾಜ್ಯದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಬಳ್ಳಾರಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸುತ್ತಮುತ್ತಲಿನ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು, ತಮಿಳುನಾಡಿನೊಂದಿಗೆ ಹೊಸೂರು ಮತ್ತು ಆನೇಕಲ್ ಸುತ್ತಮುತ್ತಲಿನ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ರಾಜ್ಯದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸೇರ್ಪಡೆಗೊಳಿಸುವುದಕ್ಕೋಸ್ಕರ ಕನ್ನಡಿಗರು ಹೋರಾಟ ನಡೆಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

✓ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ನಡುವಿನ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದ:

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ನಡುವಿನ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಬಿಂದು ಎಂದರೆ ಅದು ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆ. ರಾಜ್ಯ ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡಣಾ ಆಯೋಗದ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿಯನ್ನು ಅಂದಿನ ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರ್ಪಡೆಗೊಳಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಇದರಂತೆ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ, ಕಾರವಾರಗಳು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಉಳಿದುಕೊಂಡವು. ಆದರೆ ಕನ್ನಡ ಭಾಷೆಯನ್ನೇ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿ ಮಾತನಾಡುವಂತಹ ಸೊಲ್ಲಾಪುರ, ಜತ್ತ ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕು, ಚಂದಗಡ, ಮಂಗಳವಾಡ, ಅಕ್ಕಲಕೋಟೆ, ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಸೊಲ್ಲಾಪುರ, ಶಿರೋಳ, ಗಡಹಿಂಗ್ಲಜ ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕುಗಳು, ಉಸ್ತಾನಾಬಾದ್ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯ ನೆಳದುರ್ಗ, ಉದುರ್ಗ ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕುಗಳು, ಇವುಗಳೆಲ್ಲವೂ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರದೆ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿವೆ ಇವುಗಳನ್ನು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರ್ಪಡೆಗೊಳಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ಹೋರಾಟಗಳು ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಲೇ ಇವೆ.

✓ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಮತ್ತು ಆಂಧ್ರಪ್ರದೇಶ ನಡುವಿನ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದ:

ಕನ್ನಡ ಭಾಷೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರಧಾನವಾಗಿ ಮಾತನಾಡುವಂತಹ ಅಚ್ಚ ಕನ್ನಡದ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಾದ ಅದೋನಿ(ಆದವನಿ), ಆಲೂರು, ರಾಯದುರ್ಗ, ಮಡಕಶಿರ, ಕಲ್ಯಾಣದುರ್ಗ, ಹಿಂದೂಪುರ ಇನ್ನು ಮುಂತಾದ ಕನ್ನಡ ಭಾಷೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾತನಾಡುವ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ಆಂಧ್ರಪ್ರದೇಶ ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿ ಹೋಗಿವೆ. ಇಂದಿಗೂ ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿನ ಜನರು ಕನ್ನಡ ಅಭಿಮಾನವನ್ನು ತಮ್ಮ ಮನದಲ್ಲಿ ಮನೆ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡು ಕನ್ನಡ ಭಾಷೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯವಹರಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರ್ಪಡೆಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಇಂದಿಗೂ ಹೋರಾಟಗಳು ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಿವೆ.

✓ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಮತ್ತು ತಮಿಳುನಾಡು ನಡುವಿನ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದ:

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ದಕ್ಷಿಣದ ತುತ್ತ ತುದಿಗೆ ಅಂದರೆ ಮೈಸೂರು ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗೆ ತಾಗಿದಂತೆ ನೈರುತ್ಯ ದಿಕ್ಕಿನಲ್ಲಿರುವ ನೀಲಗಿರಿ, ಗೂಡಲೂರು, ಉದಕಮಂಡಲ(ಊಟಿ), ಕೋನೂರು, ಬೆರಂಗೂರುಗಳು, ಕೃಷ್ಣಗಿರಿ, ಹೊಸೂರು, ರಾಗಿಗುಟ್ಟಿ, ಗುಮ್ಮಳ್ಳಾಪುರ, ತಾಳವಾಡಿ ಇನ್ನೂ ಮುಂತಾದ ಕನ್ನಡ ಭಾಷೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾತನಾಡುವಂತಹ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ತಮಿಳುನಾಡು ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರ್ಪಡೆಗೊಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಇವುಗಳನ್ನು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ಹಲವಾರು ಹೋರಾಟಗಳು ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಲೇ ಇವೆ.

✓ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಮತ್ತು ಕೇರಳ ನಡುವಿನ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದ:

ಕನ್ನಡ ಭಾಷೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾತನಾಡುವಂತಹ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಾದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಕೇರಳದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಸುತ್ತಮುತ್ತಲಿನ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಾದ ಕಾಸರಗೋಡು ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕು, ಮಂಜೇಶ್ವರ, ನೀಲೇಶ್ವರ, ಹೊಸದುರ್ಗ, ಕುಂಬೈ, ವೈನಾಡು ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರ್ಪಡೆಗೊಳಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳು, ಹೋರಾಟಗಳು ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಿವೆ.

➤ ಮಹಾಜನ್ ಆಯೋಗ

ರಾಜ್ಯ ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡಣಾ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಅನುಸಾರ, ಕನ್ನಡ ಭಾಷೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾತನಾಡುವಂತಹ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳನ್ನೆಲ್ಲಾ ಒಟ್ಟುಗೂಡಿಸಿ ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಎಂದು ರಚನೆ ಮಾಡಲಾಯಿತು. ಆದರೆ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿಯೂ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಬೇಕು, ಬೆಳಗಾವಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮರಾಠಿ ಭಾಷೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾತನಾಡುವ ಜನರು ಬಹುಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರಿದ್ದು ಅದನ್ನು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ವರ್ಗಾಯಿಸಬೇಕು, ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಪೂರಕವಾಗಿ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿಯನ್ನು ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರ್ಪಡೆಗೊಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ, ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿಯನ್ನು ಪುನಃ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ವರ್ಗಾಯಿಸಲೇಬೇಕು ಎಂದು ತನ್ನ ಹಠವನ್ನು ಹಿಡಿದು ಹೋರಾಟವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಾರಂಭಿಸಿತು. ಆದರೂ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿಯನ್ನು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರ್ಪಡೆಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗಲಿಲ್ಲ. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಮೈಸೂರುರಾಜ್ಯದ ನಡುವೆ ಹಲವಾರು ಬಾರಿ ಗಲಭೆಗಳು, ಹಿಂಸಾಚಾರಗಳು,

ಚಳುವಳಿಗಳು ನಡೆದವು.ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯದ ನಡುವಿನ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದವು ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ದೊಡ್ಡ ಸವಾಲಾಯಿತು.

1965ರ ಜುಲೈನಲ್ಲಿ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆದ ಅಖಿಲ ಭಾರತ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಸಮಿತಿಯ ಸಮಾವೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದವನ್ನು ಬಗೆಹರಿಸಲು ಸೂಕ್ತ ಮಾರ್ಪಾಡುಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಲು ನಿರ್ಣಯಿಸಲಾಗಿತ್ತು. ದಿನಾಂಕ:23-5-1966ರಂದು ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಕಾರ್ಯಕಾರಿ ಸಮಿತಿಯು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ -ಮೈಸೂರು- ಕೇರಳ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದವನ್ನು ಬಗೆಹರಿಸಲು ಏಕಸದಸ್ಯ ಆಯೋಗದ ರಚನೆಗೆ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸು ಮಾಡಿತು. 1966ರ ಜುಲೈ 5ರಂದು ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಗೃಹ ಮಂತ್ರಿ ವೈ.ಬಿ.ಚೌಹಾಣ್ ರವರು ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಕಾರ್ಯಕಾರಿ ಸಮಿತಿಯ ನಿರ್ಣಯವು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದ ನಿರ್ಣಯವೆಂದು ಒಪ್ಪಿಕೊಂಡು, ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಬದ್ಧವಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಿಕೆ ಕೊಟ್ಟರು. 1966ರ ಆಗಸ್ಟ್ 14ರಂದು ಉದ್ದೇಶಿತ ಏಕಸದಸ್ಯ ಆಯೋಗದ ತೀರ್ಮಾನಗಳಿಗೆ ಎರಡು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳು ಬದ್ಧವಾಗಿರತಕ್ಕದ್ದು ಎಂದು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸಿದರು.ಅಕ್ಟೋಬರ್ 9ರಂದು ನಡೆದ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಕಾರ್ಯಕಾರಿ ಸಮಿತಿ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಮೈಸೂರು, ಮೈಸೂರು ಮತ್ತು ಕೇರಳ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ನಡುವಿನ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದವನ್ನು ಸಂಬಂಧಿತ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳೊಡನೆ ಚರ್ಚಿಸಿ ಅಂತಿಮವಾಗಿ ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸಲು ಏಕಸದಸ್ಯ ಆಯೋಗವನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಲು ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಮನವಿ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿತು.ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ನ ಪ್ರಧಾನ ಕಾರ್ಯದರ್ಶಿಯಾದ ಸಾಧಿಕ್‌ಅಲಿ ಏಕಸದಸ್ಯ ಆಯೋಗದ ತೀರ್ಮಾನವೇ ಅಂತಿಮವೆಂದು ಮತ್ತು ಏಕಸದಸ್ಯ ಆಯೋಗವು ನೀಡುವ ತೀರ್ಮಾನ, ಮೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳು ಬದ್ಧವಾಗಿರಬೇಕೆಂದು ಪ್ರಕಟಿಸಿದರು.ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದ ಮುಖ್ಯಮಂತ್ರಿ ಆಗಿದ್ದ ವಿ. ಪಿ. ನಾಯಕ್ ರವರು ಏಕಸದಸ್ಯ ಆಯೋಗದ ತೀರ್ಮಾನವೇ ಅಂತಿಮವೆಂದು, ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ತಮ್ಮ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಒಪ್ಪುವುದೆಂದು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸಿದರು.ಈ ತೀರ್ಮಾನಕ್ಕೆ ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯವು ಸಹ ತನ್ನ ಸಹಮತವನ್ನು ಸೂಚಿಸಿತು. ಗಡಿವಿವಾದವನ್ನು ಇತ್ಯರ್ಥಪಡಿಸುವುದಕ್ಕೋಸ್ಕರ ಆಗಿನ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಗೃಹ ಸಚಿವರಾದ ವೈ.ಬಿ.ಚೌಹಾಣ್ ಅವರು 22-10-1966ರಲ್ಲಿ ಸುಪ್ರೀಂಕೋರ್ಟ್ ನ ನಿವೃತ್ತ ನ್ಯಾಯಮೂರ್ತಿಯಾದ ಮೆಹರ್‌ಚಂದ್ ಮಹಾಜನ್ ರವರ ನೇತೃತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಏಕವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಆಯೋಗವನ್ನು ನೇಮಿಸಿದರು.

❖ ಮಹಾಜನ್ ಆಯೋಗದ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಚರಣೆ

1. ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಅಧಿಕೃತ ರಾಜ್ಯಪತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ(ಗೆಜೆಟ್) ದಿನಾಂಕ:25ಅಕ್ಟೋಬರ್1966ರಂದು ಅಧಿಸೂಚನೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊರಡಿಸುವುದರ ಮುಖಾಂತರ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಮೈಸೂರು ಹಾಗೂ ಮೈಸೂರು ಮತ್ತು ಕೇರಳ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ನಡುವಿನ ಗಡಿತೆಗಳನ್ನು ಬಗೆಹರಿಸುವ ಕುರಿತು ಏಕಸದಸ್ಯ ಆಯೋಗವನ್ನಾಗಿ, ಮಹಾಜನ್ ಆಯೋಗವನ್ನು ನೇಮಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಅಧಿಸೂಚನೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊರಡಿಸಲಾಯಿತು.
2. ಮಹಾಜನ್ ಆಯೋಗವು ದಿನಾಂಕ:15ನವೆಂಬರ್1966ರಂದು ತನ್ನ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಚರಣೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರಾರಂಭಿಸಿತು.
3. ಆಯೋಗವು ದಿನಾಂಕ:22ನವೆಂಬರ್1966ರಂದು ಪತ್ರಿಕಾ ಪ್ರಕಟಣೆಯನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಿ, ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ಬಗೆಹರಿಸುವ ಕುರಿತು ಹಾಗೂ ಭಾಷಿಕ ಏಕರೂಪತೆಯನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸುವಂತಹ ಹೊಸ ಗಡಿರೇಖೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುವ ಸಲುವಾಗಿ ಸಲಹೆ ಮತ್ತು ಮನವಿಗಳನ್ನು ಸಲ್ಲಿಸುವಂತೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರಿಗೆ, ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳಿಗೆ, ಹಾಗೂ ಸಂಬಂಧಪಟ್ಟ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳಿಗೆ ಆಹ್ವಾನಿಸಿತು.
4. ಆಯೋಗವು ಸಂಬಂಧಪಟ್ಟ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ತಮ್ಮ ವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ಪುಷ್ಟೀಕರಿಸುವ ಹೇಳಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅಂಕಿ-ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಗಳ ಸಹಿತ ಹಾಗೂ ಯೋಜಿತ ಗಡಿರೇಖೆಗಳ ನಕ್ಷೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸಹಿತ ಮಹಾಜನ್ ಆಯೋಗಕ್ಕೆ ದಿನಾಂಕ:15.01.1967ರ ಒಳಗೆ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸುವಂತೆ ಅಧಿಸೂಚನೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊರಡಿಸಲಾಯಿತು.
5. ಗಡಿ ವಿವಾದಕ್ಕೆ ಒಳಗಾದ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿನ ಸಂಸತ್ತಿನ ಸದಸ್ಯರಿಗೆ, ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆಯ ಶಾಸಕರುಗಳಿಗೆ, ವಿವಿಧ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಧುರೀಣರಿಗೆ, ತಮ್ಮ ತಮ್ಮ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಗಳನ್ನು, ಯೋಜಿತ ಗಡಿರೇಖೆಯನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡ ನಕ್ಷೆಗಳ ಸಹಿತ ತಮ್ಮ ಸಲಹೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸೂಚನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಆಯೋಗಕ್ಕೆ ದಿನಾಂಕ:15.01.1967ರ ಒಳಗೆ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸುವಂತೆ ಪ್ರಕಟಿಸಲಾಯಿತು.
6. ಆಯೋಗವು ಒಟ್ಟು2,240 ಮನವಿಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ವೀಕರಿಸಿತು, ಒಟ್ಟು7572 ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕವಾಗಿಯೂ, ಸಾಂಘಿಕವಾಗಿಯೂ ಸಂದರ್ಶಿಸಿತು ಮತ್ತು 3240 ಬೇಡಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ವೀಕರಿಸಿತು.
7. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪ್ರಾಂತೀಕರಣ ಸಮಿತಿ ಅಧ್ಯಕ್ಷರಾದ ಬಿ.ಎಸ್.ಕಕ್ಕಿಲಾಯ ರವರು ಕಾಸರಗೋಡು ಮೈಸೂರಿಗೆ ವರ್ಗಾಯಿಸುವಂತೆ ಅಂಕಿ ಅಂಶಗಳ ಸಮೇತ ಮನವಿ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿದರು.
8. ಆಯೋಗವು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳು ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿದ ಮತ್ತು ಮಂಡಿಸಿದ ವಾದಗಳಲ್ಲಿನ ಸತ್ಯಾಂಶವನ್ನು ಅರಿಯಲು, ಗಡಿಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳ ವಾಸ್ತವತೆಯನ್ನು ಮನಗಾಣಲೆಂದು, ಗಡಿಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಿಗೆ ಭೇಟಿ ನೀಡಿ, ಭೌಗೋಳಿಕವಾಸ್ತವಾಂಶ ಮತ್ತು ವಾದಗ್ರಸ್ತ ನಗರ ಮತ್ತು ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಭಾಗಗಳ ಪರಿಚಯಾತ್ಮಕ ಪರಿಶೀಲನೆಗಾಗಿ, ವಿವಿಧ ಸ್ಥಳಗಳನ್ನು ವಿವಿಧ ಸಮಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭೇಟಿ ನೀಡಿ ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಿ ಸಂದರ್ಶಿಸಿತು.

9. ಆಯೋಗವು ವಾದ-ವಿವಾದ ಮತ್ತು ಮನವಿಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಿ ಅಂತಿಮವಾಗಿ 196 ಪುಟಗಳುಳ್ಳ ವರದಿಯನ್ನು ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಗೃಹ ಸಚಿವಾಲಯಕ್ಕೆ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿತ್ತು.

✚ **ಗಡಿ ತಂಟೆಗಳ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆ (ಮಹಾಜನ್ ಆಯೋಗದ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಗಡಿ ವಿವಾದಗಳಿಗೆ ಕಾರಣಗಳು)**

ಮಹಾಜನ್ ಆಯೋಗವು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ-ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಹಾಗೂ ಕೇರಳ-ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ನಡುವಿನ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ಇತ್ಯರ್ಥ ಪಡಿಸುವ ಮೊದಲು, ಈ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣಿಭೂತವಾದ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡಿ ತಮ್ಮ ವರದಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಕೆಳಕಂಡಂತೆ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸಿದೆ.

1. ರಾಜ್ಯ ಪುನರ್ ರಚನಾ ಆಯೋಗಕ್ಕೆ ಭಾಷಾವಾರು ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯಗಳ ರಚನೆಯ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಗತಿಗಳನ್ನು, ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯನ್ನು, ವಾಸ್ತವಾಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಹಾಗೂ ಇವುಗಳ ಸಂಬಂಧದಲ್ಲಿ ತಳುಕು ಹಾಕಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರಬಲ್ಲ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸಂಗತಿಗಳನ್ನು ತನಿಖೆ ಮಾಡಬೇಕು ಎಂದು ಆದೇಶಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಆದರೆ ಪುನರ್ ರಚನಾ ಆಯೋಗವು, ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಾಸ್ತವಾಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಕಡೆಗಣಿಸಿತು. ಇದು ನಂತರದ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳಿಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಯಿತು.

2. ರಾಜ್ಯ ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು ಗಡಿರೇಖೆಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುವಾಗ ಒಂದು ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕನ್ನು ಅವಿಭಾಜ್ಯ ಘಟಕವನ್ನಾಗಿ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಂಡಿತು. ಭಾಷಾವಾರು ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯಗಳ ಮರುವಿಂಗಡಣೆಗೆ ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಹೋಬಳಿ ಅಥವಾ ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳನ್ನು ಘಟಕವನ್ನಾಗಿ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಂಡು ಭಾಷಾವಾರು ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ರಚನೆ ಮಾಡಲಿಲ್ಲ. ಇದು ನಂತರದ ಗಡಿ ವಿವಾದಗಳಿಗೆ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಕಾರಣವಾಯಿತು.

3. ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕು ವಿಂಗಡಣೆಗೆ ಬಹುಭಾಷಿಕರ ಅಳತೆಗೋಲನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸಲಾಯಿತು, ಆದರೆ ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರನ್ನು ಹಾಗೂ ಇತರೆ ಭಾಷಿಕರನ್ನು ಕಡೆಗಣಿಸಿ ಭಾಷಾವಾರು ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ವಿಂಗಡಣೆ ಮಾಡಲಾಯಿತು ಇದರಿಂದ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳು ಉದ್ಭವವಾದವು.

4. ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದ ಸಮಗ್ರತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಏಕಾತ್ಮಕತೆಯ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನದಿಂದ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು ಕೇವಲ ಆಡಳಿತದ ಅನುಕೂಲದ ಅಂಶವನ್ನು ಮಾತ್ರ ಪರಿಗಣಿಸಿ, ಇತರೆ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಲಕ್ಷಿಸಿ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡಿಸಿ ರಚಿಸಿತು. ಇದರಿಂದ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳು ಉದ್ಭವವಾದವು.

5. ರಾಜ್ಯ ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯಗಳ ಮರುವಿಂಗಡಣೆಗೆ ಪರಿಗಣಿಸಬೇಕಾದ ಭಾಷೆ, ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ - ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆ, ಜನಾಂಗಮೊದಲಾದ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಕಡೆಗಣಿಸಿತ್ತು.

6. ರಾಜ್ಯ ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು “ಒಂದು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಒಂದೇ ಭಾಷೆ” ಎಂಬ ಸಂಕಲ್ಪನೆಯ ತತ್ವವನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸಿತು.

7. ರಾಜ್ಯ ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು ಗಡಿಗಳ ಭವಿಷ್ಯ ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುವಾಗ ಕೇವಲ ಭಾಷಿಕ ಸಂಖ್ಯಾಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾತ್ರ ನಿರ್ಣಯಾಧಾರವಾಗಿ ಪರಿಗಣಿಸಿತು ಹಾಗೂ ಗಡಿರೇಖೆಯ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ಬಹುಸಂಖ್ಯಾತವಾಗಿ ಒಂದೇ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಭಾಷೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂಬ ಅಂಶವನ್ನು ಕಡೆಗಣಿಸಿತ್ತು.

8. ದಿನಾಂಕ:30-11-1960ರಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ನಡುವಿನ ಗಡಿ ವಿವಾದವನ್ನು ಬಗೆಹರಿಸಲು ನೇಮಕವಾದ ನಾಲ್ಕು ಜನ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳ ಸಮಿತಿಯು (ಶ್ರೀಹೆಚ್.ವಿ.ಪಾಟೀಸ್ಕರ್, ಶ್ರೀ.ಎಂ.ಡಿ.ಭಟ್,ಶ್ರೀ.ಎಸ್.ಚೆನ್ನಯ್ಯ, ಶ್ರೀ.ಎಸ್. ಎಸ್. ಮಳಿಮಲ್) ಸದರಿ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದವನ್ನು ಶಾಂತಿಯುತವಾಗಿ ಇತ್ಯರ್ಥಪಡಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಫಲವಾದದ್ದು, ಈ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳ ಮುಂದುವರೆಯುವಿಕೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಯಿತು.

9. ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಕಾರಣಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಭಾವ (ಕೆಲವು ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಸ್ವಾರ್ಥಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಕರಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ). ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ

➤ **ಮಹಾಜನ್ ಆಯೋಗದ ವರದಿಯ ಸಂಕ್ಷಿಪ್ತ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆ**

1. ಮಹಾಜನ್ ಆಯೋಗವು ದಿನಾಂಕ:25ಆಗಸ್ಟ್1967ರಂದು ತನ್ನ ವರದಿಯನ್ನು ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿದ್ದು, ಈ ವರದಿಯು ಒಟ್ಟು ನಾಲ್ಕು ಭಾಗಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದ್ದು, 196 ಪುಟಗಳಿಂದ ಕೂಡಿದೆ. ಆಯೋಗವು ತನ್ನವರದಿಯ ಮೊದಲನೇ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ, ಆಯೋಗದ ರಚನೆ, ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳು, ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆ, ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳ ತಂಟೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಕಾರಣಗಳು, ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ವಾದಗಳು, ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯದ ವಾದಗಳು, ಕೇರಳ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ವಾದಗಳು, ಈ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ಇತ್ಯರ್ಥಪಡಿಸಲು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡ ರೀತಿ-ನೀತಿಗಳನ್ನು ವಿವರಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

2. ಎರಡನೇ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿನ ವಿವಾದಿತ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಾದ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆ, ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯ-ಚಿಕ್ಕೋಡಿ ತಾಲೂಕು, ಹುಕ್ಕೇರಿ ತಾಲೂಕು, ಅಥಣಿ ತಾಲೂಕು, ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ ತಾಲೂಕು(ನಗರ ಪ್ರದೇಶ), ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ ತಾಲೂಕು(ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ), ಖಾನಾಪುರ, ಉತ್ತರ ಕನ್ನಡ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆ(ಕಾರವಾರ), ಬೀದರ್ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆ, ಗುಲ್ಬರ್ಗ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆ, ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರರಾಜ್ಯದ ಕೊಲ್ಲಾಪುರ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯ(ಚಿಂದಗಡ ತಾಲೂಕು),

ಸೊಲ್ಲಾಪುರಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯ(ಉತ್ತರ ಸಲ್ಲಾಪುರ) ಮುಂತಾದ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಕುಲಂಕುಶವಾಗಿ ವಾದ-ವಿವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಿ ತನ್ನ ವರದಿಯನ್ನು ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿದೆ.

3. ಮೂರನೇ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕಕ್ಕೆ, ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯದಿಂದ ವರ್ಗಾವಣೆ ಮಾಡಬೇಕೆಂದು ಕೊಡಮಾಡಿದಂತಹ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳ ವಿವರಗಳು, ಅವುಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಆಯೋಗವು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಿ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಂಡ ತೀರ್ಮಾನಗಳು, ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿನ ವಿವಾದಿತ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಾದ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಸೊಲ್ಲಾಪುರ ತಾಲೂಕು, ಮಂಗಳವೇಡೆ ತಾಲೂಕು, ಅಕ್ಕಲಕೋಟೆ ತಾಲೂಕು, ಸಾಂಗ್ಲಿ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯ ಜತ್ತ ತಾಲೂಕು, ಶಿರೋಳ ತಾಲೂಕು, ಗಡಹಿಂಗ್ಲಜ ತಾಲೂಕು ಮುಂತಾದವುಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಕುಲಂಕುಶವಾಗಿ ವಾದ-ವಿವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಿ, ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಂಡ ತೀರ್ಮಾನಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಈ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸನ್ನು ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿದೆ.

4. ನಾಲ್ಕನೇ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಕೇರಳ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ನಡುವಿನ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ವಿವರಿಸಿದ್ದು, ಕೇರಳದಿಂದ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕಕ್ಕೆ ಬರಬೇಕಾದ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು, ಅವುಗಳ ವಿವರಗಳು, ಅವುಗಳ ಕುರಿತಾದ ಹಕ್ಕು ಮಂಡನೆ, ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾವನೆಗಳು, ಕಾಸರಗೋಡು ತಾಲೂಕು, ಮಂಗಳೂರು ಸುತ್ತಮುತ್ತಲಿನ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ಇತ್ಯಾದಿಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಕುಲಂಕುಶವಾಗಿ ಪರಿಶೀಲನೆ ನಡೆಸಿ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿದ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸುಗಳು, ಅಂತಿಮವಾಗಿ ಆಯೋಗದ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸುಗಳ ಕ್ರೋಡೀಕೃತ ಸಾರಾಂಶದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಈ ಆಯೋಗವು ತನ್ನ ವರದಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿದೆ.

✓ ಮಹಾಜನ್ ಆಯೋಗದ ವರದಿಯ ಸಂಕ್ಷಿಪ್ತ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸುಗಳು

1. ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯವು ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯದಿಂದ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿಯನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಂತೆ ಒಟ್ಟು 814 ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳನ್ನು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ವರ್ಗಾಯಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ಹಕ್ಕು ಸಾಧಿಸಿತು. ಆದರೆ ಆಯೋಗವು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ವಾದವನ್ನು ತಿರಸ್ಕರಿಸಿ, ಬೇಡಿಕೆ ಇಟ್ಟಿದ್ದ 814 ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳ ಪೈಕಿ ಕೇವಲ 264 ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳನ್ನು ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯದಿಂದ, ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ವರ್ಗಾಯಿಸಲು ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸು ಮಾಡಿತು.

2. ಮಹಾಜನ್ ಆಯೋಗವು ತನ್ನ ವರದಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ನಿಪ್ಪಾಣಿ, ಖಾನಾಪುರ ಮತ್ತು ನಂದಗಡ ಪಟ್ಟಣಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಂತೆ 656.33 ಚದರಮೈಲಿ ಭೂ-ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯದಿಂದ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ವರ್ಗಾಯಿಸುವಂತೆ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸು ಮಾಡಿತು. ಉಳಿದಂತೆ ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯದಿಂದ ಇತರೆ ಯಾವುದೇ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ವರ್ಗಾವಣೆ ಮಾಡುವುದನ್ನು ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸು ಮಾಡಿಲ್ಲ.

3. ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯವು ಬೀದರ್ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯ ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳ ಪೈಕಿ 22ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳನ್ನು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ವರ್ಗಾಯಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ಬೇಡಿಕೆ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿದ್ದು, ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಕೇವಲ 9ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳನ್ನು ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯದಿಂದ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ವರ್ಗಾವಣೆ ಮಾಡುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸು ಮಾಡಿತು.

4. ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಇಷ್ಟಪಟ್ಟ 516 ಹಳ್ಳಿಗಳ ಪೈಕಿ ಸೊಲ್ಲಾಪುರ ನಗರವನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡು 256 ಹಳ್ಳಿಗಳನ್ನು ಬಿಟ್ಟು, ಜತ್ತ, ಅಕ್ಕಲಕೋಟೆ ಸೇರಿತಂತೆ 1368ಚದರಮೈಲಿ ವಿಸ್ತೀರ್ಣದ, 260ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳನ್ನು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯದಿಂದ, ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ವರ್ಗಾಯಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ವರದಿ ಮಾಡಿತು.

5. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಅಕ್ಕಲಕೋಟೆ ತಾಲೂಕಿನ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳನ್ನು, ಜತ್ತ ತಾಲೂಕಿನ 44ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳನ್ನು, ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಸೊಲ್ಲಾಪುರ ತಾಲೂಕಿನ 65ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳನ್ನು, ಶಿರೋಳ ತಾಲೂಕಿನ 19ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳನ್ನು ಈ ತಕ್ಷಣವೇ ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ವರ್ಗಾಯಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ಆಯೋಗವು ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸು ಮಾಡಿತು.

6. ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡಣೆ ನಂತರ 1957ರಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯವು, ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಸ್ವತಃ 227ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳ, ಸುಮಾರು 1368ಚದರಮೈಲಿಗಳ ವಿಸ್ತೀರ್ಣವುಳ್ಳ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ವರ್ಗಾಯಿಸುವುದಾಗಿ ಘೋಷಿಸಿತು. ಆದರೆ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತದವರೆಗೂ ಆ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯವು ವರ್ಗಾಯಿಸಿಲ್ಲ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ತಕ್ಷಣವೇ ಆ ಗ್ರಾಮಗಳನ್ನು ವರ್ಗಾವಣೆ ಮಾಡಬೇಕೆಂದು ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸು ಮಾಡಲಾಗಿದೆ.

7. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದದ ಬೆನ್ನುಮೂಳೆಯಾದ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ ಕನ್ನಡದ ನೆಲೆಯಾಗಿದ್ದು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲೇ ಮುಂದುವರಿಯಬೇಕೆಂದು ವರದಿ ಮಾಡಿತು.

8. ಕೇರಳ ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಚಂದ್ರಗಿರಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪಯಸ್ವಿನಿ ನದಿಯ ಉತ್ತರದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಕಾಸರಗೋಡು ತಾಲೂಕಿನ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ಪ್ರದೇಶವನ್ನು, ಕೇರಳ ರಾಜ್ಯದಿಂದ ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕತೆಯ, ಭೌಗೋಳಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪರ್ಕ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳ ಸೌಕರ್ಯಗಳ ಲಭ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಅನುಲಕ್ಷಿಸಿ, ಕೇರಳ ರಾಜ್ಯದಿಂದ ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ವರ್ಗಾಯಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ಆಯೋಗವು ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸು ಮಾಡಿತು. ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ

ಮಹಾಜನ್ ಆಯೋಗದ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸುಗಳನ್ನು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ರಾಜ್ಯವು ಒಪ್ಪಿತು ಆದರೆ, ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯವು ತಿರಸ್ಕರಿಸಿತು. ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಕಾರಣ ಎಂದರೆ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವು ದುರಾಸೆಪಟ್ಟಿದ್ದ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರವಾರ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ದಕ್ಕಲಿಲ್ಲ. ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದ ಮುಖ್ಯಮಂತ್ರಿ ವಿ.ಪಿ.ನಾಯಕ್ ರವರು ಆಯೋಗದ ವರದಿಯು ಏಕವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ತೀರ್ಪು ಆಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಒಪ್ಪುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಿ ತಿರಸ್ಕರಿಸಿದರು. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತದವರೆಗೂ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದ ನಡುವೆ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ ಗಡಿವಿವಾದವು ಜೀವಂತವಾಗಿದೆ. ಮಹಾಜನ್ ಆಯೋಗದ ಅಧ್ಯಕ್ಷರಾದ ನ್ಯಾಯಮೂರ್ತಿ ಮಹಾಜನ್ ರವರು ವಿವಾದಿತ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಿಗೆ ಭೇಟಿ ನೀಡಿ,

ಸಂದರ್ಶಿಸಿ, ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ಸಂಗ್ರಹಿಸಿ ತಮ್ಮ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸುಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ.ಆದ್ದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ವಿವಾದಿತ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳು, ಗಡಿವಿವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ಸಾವಧಾನದಿಂದ, ಕೂಲಂಕುಶವಾಗಿ ಚರ್ಚೆ ಮಾಡಿ, ನೈಜಾಂಶವನ್ನು ಅರಿತುಕೊಂಡು, ಮಾತುಕತೆ ಮುಖಾಂತರ ಈ ಗಡಿ ವಿವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ಬಗೆಹರಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಈ ಗಡಿಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಶಾಶ್ವತವಾದ ಪರಿಹಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಕಂಡುಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ.ಆದ್ದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಈ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ, ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಮತ್ತು ಕೇರಳ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನಾಯಕರುಗಳು, ಆಡಳಿತ ನಾಯಕರುಗಳು ಹಾಗೂ ಸಂಘ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ಪದಾಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಸ್ವಾರ್ಥವನ್ನು ಬಿಟ್ಟು ಸತ್ಯಾಂಶದ ಕಡೆಗೆ ನಡೆದು, ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ಬಗೆಹರಿಸಿ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಸಹಕರಿಸಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ.

❖ ಗ್ರಂಥಮಾಲಾ

- 1) "ಮಹಾಜನ ವರದಿ(ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ -ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ - ಕೇರಳ ಗಡಿ ತಂಟೆಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ನ್ಯಾಯಮೂರ್ತಿ ಮಹರ್‌ಚಂದ್‌ಮಹಾಜನ್ ವರದಿಯ ಅನುವಾದ), ಅನುವಾದಕರು:ಅನಂತಕಲ್ಲೋಳ, ಪ್ರಕಾಶಕರು:ಅಮೋಘವಾಗ್ಮಯ, ಪ್ರಸಾರ, ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ, ಮುದ್ರಣವರ್ಷ:2006."
- 2) "ಸಮಕಾಲೀನ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ:ಚರಿತ್ರೆಯ ವಿವಿಧ ಆಯಾಮಗಳು(ಕನ್ನಡ ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ ಚರಿತ್ರೆ ಸಂಪುಟ - 6) ಪ್ರಧಾನಸಂಪಾದಕರು:ವಿಜಯ್ ಪೂರ್ಣಚ್ಚ ತಂಬಂಡ, ಸಂಪುಟ ಸಂಪಾದಕರು:ಎನ್.ಚಿನ್ನಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಸೋಸಲೆ, ಪ್ರಸಾರಾಂಗ, ಕನ್ನಡ ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ, ಹಂಪಿ, ಮುದ್ರಣವರ್ಷ:2010.
- 3) "ಗಡಿಚಳುವಳಿಗಳು - ಏಕೀಕರಣೋತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಚಳುವಳಿಗಳು", (ಸಂಪುಟ - 1), ಎನ್.ಚಿನ್ನಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಸೋಸಲೆ, ಪ್ರಸಾರಾಂಗ, ಕನ್ನಡವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ, ಹಂಪಿ, ಮುದ್ರಣವರ್ಷ:2014.
- 4) "ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಏಕೀಕರಣ ಇತಿಹಾಸ", (ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯ ಅಕಾಡೆಮಿ ಪ್ರಶಸ್ತಿ ಪುರಸ್ಕೃತ ಕೃತಿ) ಡಾ.ಎಚ್.ಎಸ್.ಗೋಪಾಲ್ ರಾವ್, ನವಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪಬ್ಲಿಕೇಶನ್ಸ್ ಪ್ರೈವೇಟ್ ಲಿಮಿಟೆಡ್, ಎಂಟನೇ ಮುದ್ರಣ:2018.
- 5) "ಏಕೀಕರಣ ಚಳುವಳಿ ಮತ್ತು ಬಳ್ಳಾರಿ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆ:ಕನ್ನಡಿಗರ ಚಾರಿತ್ರಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಜಾಗೃತಿ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆ", ಡಾ.ವಿರುಪಾಕ್ಷ ಪೂಜಾರಹಳ್ಳಿ, ಪ್ರಸಾರಂಗ, ಕನ್ನಡ ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ, ಹಂಪಿ, ಮುದ್ರಣವರ್ಷ:2014.
- 6) "ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯೋತ್ತರ ಭಾರತ", (ಪ್ರೊಫೆಸರ್.ಬಿಪಿನ್‌ಚಂದ್ರ,ಪ್ರೊಫೆಸರ್.ಮೃದುಲಾ ಮುಖರ್ಜಿ,ಪ್ರೊಫೆಸರ್.ಆದಿತ್ಯ ಮುಖರ್ಜಿ), ಕನ್ನಡಕ್ಕೆ ಅನುವಾದ ಡಾ.ಸಿ.ಬಿ.ಕಮಲಾ, ನವ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪಬ್ಲಿಕೇಶನ್ಸ್ ಪ್ರೈವೇಟ್ ಲಿಮಿಟೆಡ್ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು, ಮುದ್ರಣವರ್ಷ:2019.
- 7) "ಭಾರತದ ಭಾಷಿಕ ಸನ್ನಿವೇಶ - ಅಂಬೇಡ್ಕರ್‌ಭಾಷಿಕ ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳು", ಮೇಟಿ ಮಲ್ಲಿಕಾರ್ಜುನ, ಕ್ರಿಯಾ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಪ್ರೈವೇಟ್‌ಲಿಮಿಟೆಡ್, ಮುದ್ರಣವರ್ಷ:2019.
- 8) "ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವಿಭಾಗಗಳು", ಡಾ.ಚನ್ನಬಸವಯ್ಯ ಹಿರೇಮಠ, ಪ್ರಸಾರಂಗ, ಕನ್ನಡ ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ, ಹಂಪಿ, ಮುದ್ರಣವರ್ಷ:2014.
- 9) "ಕನ್ನಡ - ಕನ್ನಡಿಗ- ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ", ಎಲ್.ಎಸ್.ಶೇಷಗಿರಿರಾವ್, ಎಂ.ಚಿದಾನಂದಮೂರ್ತಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾ.ನಂ.ಚಂದ್ರಶೇಖರ್, ಸಪ್ತಬುಕ್‌ಹೌಸ್, ಮೂರನೇ ಮುಖ್ಯರಸ್ತೆ, ಗಾಂಧಿನಗರ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು, 9ನೇ ಮುದ್ರಣ, 2012.
- 10) "ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಇತಿಹಾಸ" (ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಇತಿಹಾಸ), ಕೆ.ಎನ್.ಅಶ್ವತ್ಥಪ್ಪ, ಪ್ರಕಾಶಕರು: ಸುಭಾಷ್ ಸೋರ್ಸೆ, ಅವೆನ್ಯೂ ರೋಡ್, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು:560 002.

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ

ಸೋಮಶೇಖರ ಎನ್.ಸಿ

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ಪೀಠಿಕೆ

ಯಾವುದೇ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಗೆ ಯಶಸ್ವಿಯಾಗಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಅಲ್ಲಿನ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಬಹಳ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ನಮ್ಮ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಕ್ಷಪಾತ ಮತ್ತು ನಮ್ಮ ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಅನುಸಾರವಾಗಿ ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಕಾಲಕಾಲಕ್ಕೆ ನಿಯತಕಾಲಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ನಡೆಸುವುದರ ಮೂಲಕ ಮತ್ತು ಶಾಂತಿಯುತ ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ಬದಲಾಯಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯನ್ನು ನಡೆಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಬಂದಿದ್ದೇವೆ. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಅನೇಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ನೋಡಬಹುದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಅಧ್ಯಕ್ಷರ ಚುನಾವಣೆ, ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆ, ರಾಜ್ಯಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆ, ಎಲ್ಲಾ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಾವು ನೋಡಬಹುದು. ಈ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಅನೇಕ ಧರ್ಮ ಜಾತಿ ಭಾಷೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತ ಆಧಾರಿತವಾಗಿ ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುವ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳು ಸಮಾನ ಅವಕಾಶವನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತಗಳನ್ನು ಆಧರಿಸಿ ಜಾತಿ ಧರ್ಮ ಮತ್ತು ಭಾಷೆಗೆ ಒಳಗೊಂಡ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಜಾತಿಯ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರವೇಶಕ್ಕೆ ಆದ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವಂಥ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳು ಯಾವುದೇ ಧರ್ಮ ಆಧಾರಿತವಾಗಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಅವಕಾಶವನ್ನು ನೀಡಿರುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಒಕ್ಕಲಿಗ ಜಾತಿಗಳು ಪ್ರಬಲವಾಗಿವೆ 1970ರಲ್ಲಿ ಆರಂಭ ತನಕಾಧಿಕಾರ ರಾಜಕಾರಣವು ಪ್ರಬಲವಾದ ಜಾತಿಗಳು ಹೊಸ ಹೊಸ ಜಾತಿಗಳು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಯಾಗುತ್ತ ಆ ಜಾತಿಗಳು ಸಮಾಜದ ಅಂಗಳದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಅವಕಾಶಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ನಿರಂತರವಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಖಾಮುಖಿಯಾಗಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ರಾಜಕಾರಣವು ಬದಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. 2024ರಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲವು ಜಾತಿಗಳು ಸೀಮಿತವಾದ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೊಂದಿದೆ.

ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ

ಭಾರತವು ವಿಶ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ದೊಡ್ಡ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ದೇಶವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಅನೇಕ ಧರ್ಮಗಳಾದ ಹಿಂದೂ, ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ, ಕ್ರೈಸ್ತ, ಸಿಖ್, ಪಾರ್ಸಿ, ಬೌದ್ಧ ಮತ್ತು ಜೈನ ಧರ್ಮಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಧರ್ಮಗಳು ಒಂದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ಸಮಾನತೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಿರುವುದು ನಮ್ಮ ದೇಶದ ವಿಶೇಷತೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ನಮ್ಮ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಥವಾ ಧರ್ಮದ ಮತ್ತು ಜಾತಿ ಭಾಷೆ, ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ, ಆಧರಿಸಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲೂ ಸಮಾನತೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಿರುವುದು ಅಥವಾ ಸಮಾನ ಅವಕಾಶವನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ನಮ್ಮ ಮೂಲ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ನಾವು ತಿಳಿಯಬಹುದು. ಸಮಾಜದ ಎಲ್ಲರಿಗೂ ಸಮಾನ ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡಿರುವುದು. ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಧರ್ಮ ಜಾತಿ ಜನರು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಹೊಂದಲು ಅವಕಾಶವನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಇಂಗ್ಲೀಷ್‌ನಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿ ಎಂಬುದಕ್ಕೆ ಸಮಾನವಾದ ಅರ್ಥಕೊಡುವ ಪದವೆಂದರೆ Caste ಈ Caste ಪೋರ್ಚುಗೀಸ್ ಶಬ್ದವಾದ Casta ಎಂಬುದರಿಂದ ಬಂದಿದೆ. Casta ಎಂದರೆ ಜನಾಂಗ (Race) ಪೀಳಿಗೆ (Breed) ಹಾಗೂ ಕುಲ (Clan) ಮುಂತಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಲಾಗುತ್ತಿತ್ತು ಆದುದರಿಂದ ಅಭಿಣಜ ಪದವು ಶುದ್ಧ ತಳಿ ಎಂಬ ಜೈವಿಕ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರೀಯ ಪದವಾಗಿ ವ್ಯಾಪಕವಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಲ್ಪಡುತ್ತಿದೆ. 'ಜಾತಿ' ಎಂಬ ಪದವು ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತದ 'ಜನ್' ಎಂಬ ಪದದಿಂದ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಂಡಿದೆ. 'ಜನ್' ಎಂದರೆ 'ಜನಿಸುವುದು' ಅಥವಾ 'ಹುಟ್ಟುವುದು' ಎಂದು ಅರ್ಥ. ಜನ್ಮ ನೀಡಿದವಳನ್ನು 'ಜನನಿ' ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯಲಾಗುವುದು. 'ಜಾತಕ' ಎಂಬ ಪದವೂ ಹುಟ್ಟಿನ ಮತ್ತು ಹುಟ್ಟಿನ ವೇಳೆಯಿಂದ ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡ ಫಲಗಳನ್ನು ಲೆಕ್ಕಮಾಡುವ ಕ್ರಮ ಎಂದು ಅರ್ಥವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ಬ್ರಿಟಿಷರು ಕಾಲಿಟ್ಟ ನಂತರ ಜಾತಿ ಪದ್ಧತಿ ಒಂದು ಹೊಸತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಿತು. ಭಾರತದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಗತಿಗಳು ಹೊಸ ಆಕಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲಾರಂಭಿಸಿದವು. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿದ್ದ ನೂರಾರು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ ಒಂದೂಗೊಡಿಸಿ ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ಬ್ರಿಟಿಷರ ಚಕ್ರಾಧಿಪತ್ಯದ ಆಡಳಿತಕ್ಕೊಳಪಡಿಸಿದರು. ಈ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಒಗ್ಗೂಡುವಿಕೆಯಿಂದ ಬ್ರಿಟಿಷ್ ಆಡಳಿತಗಾರರು ಇಡೀ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ಅನ್ವಯ- ವಾಗುವಂತಹ ಅನೇಕ ಶಾಸನಗಳನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸಿ, ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಿದರು. ಮೊದಲಿಗೆ ಜಾತಿ ಅನರ್ಹತಾ ನಿವಾರಣಾ ಶಾಸನ 1850, ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮೇಲು-ಕೀಳುಗಳನ್ನು ತೊಡೆದು ಹಾಕಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸಲಾಯಿತು.

ಆದರೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯು ಮಾನವರ ವರ್ತನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಸಂರಚನೆಗಳನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ, ನಿಯಂತ್ರಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಎಂಬ ಪದ ಪ್ರಯೋಗವು ಸಹ 'ಸರ್ಕಾರದ' ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳಿಗೂ ಅನ್ವಯಿಸುವುದು, ರಾಜಕೀಯ

ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಸಕಲ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯಾಡಳಿತಕ್ಕೆ ಅನ್ವಯಿಸುವಂತೆ ಈ ಪದವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ವ್ಯಾಪಕವಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ನಡೆಸಲು ಅನೇಕ ವಿಧಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಬಳಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರಾರಂಭದಲ್ಲಿ 'ಅಧಿಕಾರವು' ಅನೌಪಚಾರಿಕ ನಿಯಮಗಳಿಂದ ಏರ್ಪಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ 'ಜಾತಿ ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಗಳು' ಇಂತಹ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದವು. ಜಾತಿ ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಗಳು ಜಾತಿ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ನಿಯಮಗಳನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದವಲ್ಲದೆ, ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ಉಲ್ಲಂಘಿಸಿದವರಿಗೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷಿಸುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದವು. ಆದರೆ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ನಂತರ ಭಾರತವು "ಸಾರ್ವಭೌಮಾಧಿಕಾರ ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಧರ್ಮನಿರಪೇಕ್ಷಿತ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಆಡಳಿತ" ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾಗಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವು ವೈಚಾರಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯಬದ್ಧ ವಿಧಾನ ಹಾಗೂ ಸೃಜನಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ವಿಧಾನಗಳ ಸಂಮಿಶ್ರಣವಾಗಿದೆ. ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಆಡಳಿತ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಆಯ್ಕೆಗೊಂಡ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಯು ತನ್ನನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡಿ ಕಳುಹಿಸುವ ಮತದಾರರಿಗೆ, ಪ್ರತಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲೂ ತನ್ನ ಬದ್ಧತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯನ್ನು ಸಿದ್ಧಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. 'ಚುನಾವಣೆ' ಯ ಮೂಲಕ ಮತದಾರರು ತಮ್ಮ ಚುನಾಯಿತ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳಿಗೆ ವರ್ಗಾಯಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಆದರೆ ಈ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟವರು ಸರ್ವಸಮ್ಮತ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯಾಗಿರುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ತನ್ನ ನಿಕಟ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಗಿಂತ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಮತಗಳನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆಯಾಗಿರುತ್ತಾನೆ. ಆದರೆ ಪತಿನಿಧಿಯು ತನ್ನ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದ ಅತ್ಯುತ್ತಮ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಪಡೆದಿರುವನಲ್ಲದೆ, ತನ್ನ ಮತದಾರರ, ಉನ್ನತ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಕಾಪಾಡಲು ಬದ್ಧನಾಗಿರುತ್ತಾನೆ. ಅನೇಕ ವೇಳೆ ಅನೇಕ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಜನಪ್ರಿಯವಾಗಿಲ್ಲದಿರಬಹುದು. ಹೀಗಾಗಿ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಯೊಬ್ಬನು ತನ್ನ ಮತದಾರರ ಭಾವನೆಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸೂಕ್ಷ್ಮ ರೀತಿಯ ಸ್ಪಂದನ ಹೊಂದಿರಬೇಕು. "ಪ್ರಜಾ-ಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ" ದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಸಮಾನತೆಯ ಭಾವನೆಯೇ ಅದರ ವೈಶಿಷ್ಟ್ಯತೆ ಎನ್ನಬಹುದು. ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ನಾಗರಿಕನೊಬ್ಬ ಮತ ಚಲಾಯಿಸುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ನಾಗರಿಕನ ಗೌರವ, ಘನತೆ, ಸಮಾನತೆ, ಮುಂತಾದವುಗಳನ್ನು ಜೀವಂತವಾಗಿರಿಸುವ ಕ್ರಮವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ.

ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪಕ್ಷವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆ ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಮತದಾರ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯು ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಉಳಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುತ್ತದೆ ಮತದಾರ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರವೊಂದರಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾರರ ಸ್ವಭಾವ ಸ್ವರೂಪಗಳು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ನೇರ ಪರಿಣಾಮ ಬೀರುತ್ತವೆ. ಈ ಮತದಾರ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ ಧರ್ಮ, ವರ್ಗ ಮುಂತಾದವು ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡುವುದರಿಂದ ಹಿಡಿದು ಮತದಾನ ಮಾಡುವಿಕೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ರಚಿಸುವಿಕೆ, ಸರ್ಕಾರ- ವನ್ನು ಉರುಳಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಮುಂತಾದ ಎಲ್ಲ ಹಂತಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಭಾವಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಹುಸಂಖ್ಯಾತ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿವೆ. ಇವು ನಾನಾರೀತಿಯ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಪ್ರಣಾಲಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸಿದ್ಧಪಡಿಸಿವೆ. ಅಲ್ಲದೆ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯಾನಂತರದ ಈ 74ವರ್ಷಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ ಅಪಾರವಾಗಿ ವೃದ್ಧಿಗೊಂಡು ಭಾರತೀಯ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ನಾನಾ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹುಟ್ಟು ಹಾಕಿವೆ, ಮತ್ತು ವರ್ಗ, ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಮುಂತಾದವುಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆ ನೀಡುತ್ತವೆ ಎನ್ನಬಹುದು, ಭಾರತದಂತಹ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಪರ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು, ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಭವಿಷ್ಯವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಅಪಾರ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರಬಲ್ಲವು.

ಪ್ರಾರಂಭದ ವರ್ಷಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾರರು ತಮ್ಮನ್ನು ತಾವೇ ಆಳಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡುವಲ್ಲಿ ಅನೇಕ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನೆದುರಿಸಿದರು. ಆದರೆ ಕಳೆದ ವರ್ಷಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅನೇಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು, ಅನೇಕ ಹಂತದಲ್ಲಿ ಏರ್ಪಟ್ಟು ಮತದಾರರು ಪ್ರಬುದ್ಧತೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಎಲ್ಲ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪೂರ್ವ ಸಮೀಕ್ಷೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವುದು, ಜಾತಿ ಸಮ್ಮೇಳನಗಳನ್ನು ಏರ್ಪಡಿಸುವುದು, ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ ಪಂಗಡಗಳನ್ನು ಒಲಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಮುಂತಾದ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಏರ್ಪಡಿಸುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಅಲ್ಲದೆ ಜಾತಿಯ ಭಾವನೆಗಳು, ಸಮಗ್ರವೂ, ತೀವ್ರವೂ ಆಗಿರಲು ಎಲ್ಲ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸುತ್ತಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಜಾತಿ ಪ್ರೇಮ-ಜಾತಿ ನಿಷ್ಠೆ ಎಂದು ಇದನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸಬಹುದು. ಹೀಗಾಗಿ ಜಾತಿ-ಜಾತಿಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ಇದ ಸಾಂಪದಾಯಿಕ ಹೊಂದಾಣಿಕೆ ಮಾಯವಾಗಿ ಒಂದಕ್ಕೊಂದು ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ಹೀಗಾಗಿ ಜಾತಿ-ಜಾತಿಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ಇದ್ದ ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕ ಹೊಂದಾಣಿಕೆ ಮಾಯವಾಗಿ ಒಂದಕ್ಕೊಂದು ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಹಂತ ತಲುಪಿರುವುದಲ್ಲದೆ ಜಾತಿ ಸಂಘರ್ಷಗಳನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುತ್ತಿವೆ. ರಾಜಕಾರಣಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಗ್ರಾಮಪಂಚಾಯತಿ, ತಾಲೂಕು ಮಟ್ಟ, ಜಿಲ್ಲಾ, ರಾಜ್ಯ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಪಾರ ಒತ್ತಡ ಬೀರುವ 'ಒತ್ತಡ ಸಮೂಹ' ಗಳಾಗುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಒಕ್ಕಲಿಗರ-ಲಿಂಗಾಯಿತರ, ಕೇರಳದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಿರಿಯನ್ ಕ್ರಿಶ್ಚಿಯನ್, ನಾಯರ್‌ಗಳು, ಇಜಾರಿಗಳು, ಆಂಧ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ರೆಡ್ಡಿ-ಕಮ್ಯಾಳು ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಮರಾಠರು, ಬನಿಯಾ, ಪಟೇಲ್, ಕೋಲಿಗಳು ಬಿಹಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಭೂಮಿಹಾರ್ ಕಾಯಸ್ಥ ಮತ್ತು ರಜಪೂತ ಗುಂಪುಗಳು ಒಳಗುಂಪುಗಳು, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕಾರಣಗಳಿಗೆ ಒಂದಾಗಿ ಅನೇಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನೆದುರಿಸಿ, ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಫಲಿತಾಂಶ- ಗಳನ್ನು ಏರುಪೇರು ಮಾಡಿವೆ. ಇತ್ತೀಚೆಗೆ ನಡೆದ ಉತ್ತರ ಪ್ರದೇಶ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಇದಕ್ಕೊಂದು ಅತ್ಯುತ್ತಮ ಉದಾಹರಣೆ. ಎರಡು ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಧ್ರುವಗಳಿಗಿಂತಿದ್ದ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರು, ಅಂತಿಮರು, ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ ಒಂದಾಗಿ 'ಮಾಯಾವತಿ' ಎಂಬುವರ "ಬಹುಜನ ಸಮಾಜಪಕ್ಷ" ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಪಡೆಯುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡಿದರು. ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯಗಳ ನಡುವಣ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸುದೀರ್ಘವಾದ ವಿವರಣೆ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳ ನಡುವಿನ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳಿಗಾಗಿ ಜಾತಿಯ ವ್ಯಾಪಕ ಬಳಕೆ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಮುಂದುವರಿದು ಆಂದ್ರೆ

ಬೆತೆಯವರು 1950-60 ದಶಕಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಖಂಡರೇ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿ ಬಳಕೆಯನ್ನು ಖಂಡಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು, ಆದರೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಯಶಸ್ವಿಯಾಗಲು, ಜಾತಿಯ ಬಳಕೆ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯವೆಂದೂ ವಾದಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದರೆಂದು ಹೇಳಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ರಾಜ್ಯ ಹಾಗೂ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಜಾತಿ-ಧರ್ಮದ ಹೆಸರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ತಾರತಮ್ಯ ಮಾಡುವುದನ್ನು ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ 15 ನೇ ವಿಧಿ ತಡೆಯುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಉದ್ಯೋಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮಾನಾವಕಾಶಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಬೇಕು ಮತ್ತು ಜಾತಿ ಧರ್ಮದ ಹೆಸರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಯುವ ತಾರತಮ್ಯವನ್ನು ನಿಷೇಧಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಇಷ್ಟೆಲ್ಲ ನಿರ್ಬಂಧಗಳಿದ್ದರೂ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಓಟ್ ಬ್ಯಾಂಕುಗಳನ್ನು ದೃಷ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿರಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ರಾಜಕಾರಣ ಮಾಡಲು ಹೊರಟವೆ. ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಮೂಲ ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಅದರ ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾವನೆಯಲ್ಲಿರುವಂತೆ ನ್ಯಾಯ ಹಾಗೂ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ವರ್ಗಗಳಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕವಾಗಿ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದವರ ಏಳಿಗೆಗೆ ವಿಶೇಷ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾದ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿದೆ. ಇದರ ಬದಲು ಧರ್ಮದ, ಜಾತಿಯ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಜನಗಳನ್ನು ವಿಭಜಿಸುತ್ತಾ ಅವರ ಏಳಿಗೆಗೆ ಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಮೂಲ ಆಶಯಗಳಿಗೆ ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತ-ಬಹುಸಂಖ್ಯಾತ ಎಂದು ವಿಭಜಿಸುವುದು ದೇಶದ ಏಕತೆಗೆ ಐಕ್ಯತೆಗೆ ಧಕ್ಕೆಯುಂಟಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಜಾತ್ಯಾತೀತತೆಯ ಹೆಸರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿ ರಾಜಕಾರಣ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿರುವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳ ಚತುರಂಗ- ದಾಟವನ್ನು ಜನರು ನಿಸ್ಸಹಾಯಕರಾಗಿ ನೋಡುವಂತಾಗಿದೆ.

1970ರ ನಂತರ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮುಖಂಡರು ಮತ್ತು ಬುದ್ಧಿಜೀವಿಗಳ ಆಲೋಚನೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅನುಸರಣೆ ವಿಧಾನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗಳು ಕಂಡುಬಂದಿವೆ. ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನೀತಿಯ ತತ್ವವನ್ನಾಧರಿಸಿ ಗತಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಶೋಷಣೆಗೆ ಬಲಿಯಾಗಿದ್ದ ಕೆಳಜಾತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಜೀವನದ ಪ್ರತಿ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ವ್ಯಾಪಕ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯ ಮೂಲಕ ವಿಶೇಷ ರಕ್ಷಣೆ ನೀಡಬೇಕೆಂಬ ವಾದ ಮಂಡಿಸಲಾರಂಭಿಸಲಾಯಿತು, ಆಂಧ್ರಬೆತೆಯವರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಈ ವಾದವು ಹೊಸದಲ್ಲದಿದ್ದರೂ ಇದರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚುತ್ತಿದ್ದ ತೀವ್ರತೆ ಹೊಸದನ್ನೆಬ್ಬಿಸಿತು. ಈ 2007ರಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆದ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾಯಾವತಿ ಎಂಬ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ಮಹಿಳೆ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟ ಬಹುಮತ ಗಳಿಸಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರದ ಗದ್ದುಗೆ ಏರಿದರಿಂದ ಭಾರತದ ಅದರಲ್ಲೂ ಉತ್ತರಪ್ರದೇಶದ ರಾಜಕಾರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಜಾತಿ ಸಮೀಕರಣದ ಚಿತ್ರಣವೇ ಬದಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ಭಾರತದ ಆರಂಭದಲ್ಲಿ ದೇಶ ಕಂಡಿದ್ದು ಮೇಲ್ವರ್ಗದ ರಾಜಕಾರಣ. ನಂತರದ ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹೊಸ ಹೊಸ ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳು, ಹೊಸ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತಗಳು, ಸಮೀಕರಣಗಳು ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಮಂಡಲ್ ಹೋರಾಟದಿಂದ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಂಡದ್ದು ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ವರ್ಗಗಳ ರಾಜಕಾರಣ. ವಿಶೇಷವೆಂದರೆ ಮೇಲ್ವರ್ಗ ಹಾಗೂ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದವರು ರಾಜಕಾರಣಕ್ಕೆ ದಾಳಗಳನ್ನಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದು ದಲಿತರನ್ನು ಆದರೆ ಈಗ (2024) ರಲ್ಲಿ ಆ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಯೂ ಬದಲಾಗಿದೆ. ದಲಿತರು ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಗುದ್ದುಗೆ ಏರುವ ದಾಳಗಳಾಗುವ ಬದಲು ತಾವೇ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಪೀಠಗಳನ್ನು ತಲುಪುವ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಗೆ ತಲುಪುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಮೂಲ ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಅದರ ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾವನೆಯಲ್ಲಿರುವಂತೆ ನ್ಯಾಯ ಹಾಗೂ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ವರ್ಗಗಳಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕವಾಗಿ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದವರ ಏಳಿಗೆಗೆ ವಿಶೇಷ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾದ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿದೆ. ಬದಲಾಗುತ್ತಿರುವ ಜಾತಿಯ ರೂಪರೇಣಿಗಳು ಜಗತ್ತಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾವುದೂ ಒಂದೇ ರೀತಿಯಿಂದ, ಒಂದೇ ದಾರಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಯುವುದು ವಿರಳ, ಅದರಲ್ಲೂ ಮಾನವ ಸಮಾಜ ಕಾಲಕ್ಕನುಗುಣವಾಗಿ ಬದಲಾವಣೆ ನಡೆದಿದೆ. ಇಂತಹ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗೆ ಅನೇಕ ಕಾರಣಗಳಿವೆ. ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಹಾಗೂ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಕಾರಣಗಳೇ ಮಾನವ ಜೀವನದ ಮೇಲೆ ಅಪಾರ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುವುದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗಳಿಗೂ ಕಾರಣವಾಗುತ್ತವೆ. ಭಾರತೀಯ ಜಾತಿಪದ್ಧತಿಯು ಸಹ ಇಂತಹ ಪ್ರಭಾವಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಿಲುಕಿ ತನ್ನ ಮುಂಚಿನ ರೂಪುರೇಖೆಗಳನ್ನು ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗೆ ಒಡ್ಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದೆ.

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ

ಭಾರತದ ಇತರ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿರುವಂತೆ, ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ದೃಶ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಇತಿಹಾಸದಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿಗಳು ಉಪಜಾತಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಜಾತೀಯತೆಯು ಪ್ರಾಬಲ್ಯ ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿ, ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮಹತ್ವಾಕಾಂಕ್ಷಿಗಳಿಂದ ಒಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಹಿಡಿದಿಟ್ಟುಕೊಂಡಿರುವೆ. 2024ರ ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ, ಭಾರತೀಯ ಜನತಾ ಪಕ್ಷವು (ಬಿಜೆಪಿ) ಪಕ್ಷವು ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವ 25 ಸ್ಥಾನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮೂರು ವಕ್ರಲಿಗರು ಮತ್ತು ಒಂಬತ್ತು ಲಿಂಗಾಯತರಿಗೆ ಟಿಕೆಟ್ ನೀಡಿದೆ, ಆದರೆ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಆರು ಒಕ್ಕಲಿಗರು ಮತ್ತು ಐದು ಲಿಂಗಾಯತರನ್ನು ನಾಮನಿರ್ದೇಶನ ಮಾಡಿದೆ. ಜನತಾ ದಳ (ಜಾತ್ಯತೀತ) ತನ್ನ ಮೂರು ಸ್ಥಾನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಎರಡು ಒಕ್ಕಲಿಗರಿಗೆ ಟಿಕೆಟ್ ನೀಡಿದೆ. ಈ ಎರಡು ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳು ರಾಜ್ಯದ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಅತ್ಯಂತ 'ಪ್ರಾಬಲ್ಯ' ಎಂದು ನೋಡಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಜಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಅಧಿಕಾರದ ಸುತ್ತ ಯಾವುದೇ ಚರ್ಚೆಯ ಕೇಂದ್ರವಾಗಿದೆ. ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಮರು ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿಗಳ ಗಣನೀಯ ಜನಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯೂ ಇದೆ. 2011 ರ ಜನಗಣತಿಯ ಪ್ರಕಾರ, ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಮರು 12.92% ರಷ್ಟಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಆದರೆ, ಟಿಕೆಟ್ ಹಂಚಿಕೆ ವಿಚಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಬಂದರೆ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತ ಸಮುದಾಯವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಲಕ್ಷಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. 2019 ರ ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಂತೆ, ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಪಕ್ಷವು ಒಬ್ಬ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯನ್ನು ಮಾತ್ರ ನಾಮನಿರ್ದೇಶನ ಮಾಡಿದೆ.

ಐದು ಎಸ್‌ಸಿ ಮೀಸಲು ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಿದ್ದು, ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಪಕ್ಷವು ಇಬ್ಬರು ಎಸ್‌ಸಿ ಎಡ ಮತ್ತು ಮೂವರು ಎಸ್‌ಸಿ ಬಲ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಟಿಕೆಟ್ ನೀಡಿದ್ದು, ಬಿಜೆಪಿ ಇಬ್ಬರು ಎಸ್‌ಸಿ ಎಡ, ಒಬ್ಬ ಎಸ್‌ಸಿ ರೈಟ್ ಮತ್ತು ಲಂಬಾಣಿ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಒಬ್ಬ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯನ್ನು

ಸೂಚಿಸಿದೆ. ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಒಕ್ಕೂಟದ (ಎನ್‌ಡಿಎ) ಭಾಗವಾಗಿ ನೀಡಲಾದ ಏಕೈಕ ಮೀಸಲು ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರವಾದ ಕೋಲಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಜೆಡಿ(ಎಸ್) ಒಬ್ಬ ಭೋವಿ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯನ್ನು ಕಣಕ್ಕಿಳಿಸಿದೆ. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ದೃಶ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಒಕ್ಕಲಿಗರು ಮತ್ತು ಲಿಂಗಾಯತ ಜಾತಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಉಪ-ಜಾತಿಗಳ ಪ್ರಭಾವವು ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಮೂರು ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ - ಹಳೆಯ ಮೈಸೂರು, ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಮತ್ತು ಕರಾವಳಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಬಿಜೆಪಿಗೆ ಮಾಜಿ ಮುಖ್ಯಮಂತ್ರಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಹಿರಿಯ ನಾಯಕ ಬಿ.ಎಸ್. ಯಡಿಯೂರಪ್ಪ ಅವರು ಈ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಲಿಂಗಾಯತ ಮತದಾರರು ಪಕ್ಷದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಉಳಿಯುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಯಡಿಯೂರಪ್ಪ ಬಣಜಿಗ ಲಿಂಗಾಯತ ಉಪ-ಪಂಗಡಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿದವರು ಅವರು ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಎತ್ತರದ ನಾಯಕರಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಬಿಜೆಪಿ ಅವರಿಗೆ ಆಯ್ಕೆಯ ಪಕ್ಷವಾಗಿದೆ. ಆದಾಗ್ಯೂ, 2021 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಬಿಜೆಪಿ ವಿವರಿಸಲಾಗದ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಯಡಿಯೂರಪ್ಪ ಅವರನ್ನು ಬಸವರಾಜ ಬೊಮ್ಮಾಯಿ ಅವರನ್ನು ಮುಖ್ಯಮಂತ್ರಿಯನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡಿದ ನಂತರ ವಿಷಯಗಳು ಇತ್ತೀಚೆಗೆ ಹರಿದಾಡುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಕುತೂಹಲಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ, ಬೊಮ್ಮಾಯಿ ಕೂಡ ಲಿಂಗಾಯತರಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಯಡಿಯೂರಪ್ಪ ಪುತ್ರ ಬಿ.ವೈ. ವಿಜಯೇಂದ್ರ ಅವರು ನವೆಂಬರ್ 2023 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಬಿಜೆಪಿ ಅಧ್ಯಕ್ಷರಾಗಿ ನೇಮಕಗೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಇನ್ನೊಬ್ಬ ಪುತ್ರ ಬಿ.ವೈ. ರಾಘವೇಂದ್ರ, ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ನಾಯಕರ ವಿರೋಧದ ನಡುವೆಯೂ ಶಿವಮೊಗ್ಗ ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಿಂದ ಮರುನಾಮಕರಣ ಮಾಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಈಶ್ವರಪ್ಪ ಅವರನ್ನು ಈಗ ಪಕ್ಷದಿಂದ ಉಚ್ಚಾಟಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದು ಸಮುದಾಯ ಮತ್ತು ಬಿಜೆಪಿ ಎರಡರ ಮೇಲೂ ಒಂದು ಕುಟುಂಬದ ಶಕ್ತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಭಾವವನ್ನು ತೋರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಯಡಿಯೂರಪ್ಪ ಅವರ ಜನಪ್ರಿಯತೆಗೆ ಹೋಲಿಸಿದರೆ, ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಲಿಂಗಾಯತ ಭಾರೀ ಪ್ರಭಾವವು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸಚಿವ ಎಂ.ಬಿ. ಪಾಟೀಲ್ ಮತ್ತು ಹಿರಿಯ ನಾಯಕ ಶಾಮನೂರು ಶಿವಶಂಕರಪ್ಪ ಕ್ರಮವಾಗಿ ಬಿಜಾಪುರ ಮತ್ತು ದಾವಣಗೆರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಈ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳ ಸುತ್ತಮುತ್ತಲಿನ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಿಗೆ ಸೀಮಿತರಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ತುಮಕೂರು, ಕೋಲಾರ ಸೇರಿದಂತೆ 11 ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುವ ಹಳೇ ಮೈಸೂರು ಪ್ರದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಉತ್ತರ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಮತ್ತು ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಸೆಂಟ್ರಲ್ - ತಿಗಳ (ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ತುಮಕೂರು ಮತ್ತು ಬೆಂಗಳೂರಿನಲ್ಲಿ) ಮತ್ತು ಉಪ್ಪಾರ (ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಚಾಮರಾಜನಗರ) ಒಬಿಸಿ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳ ಪ್ರಭಾವ. ಆದರೆ ಬಹುತೇಕ ಎಲ್ಲ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ದಕ್ಷಿಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ಪ್ರಾಬಲ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಗಣನೀಯ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ ಮತ್ತು ಒಕ್ಕಲಿಗ ಮತದಾರರು ಇದ್ದಾರೆ. ಸೂರ್ಯ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿ ಸೌಮ್ಯಾ ರೆಡ್ಡಿ. ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಉತ್ತರದಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಗಳ ಮತ್ತು ಒಕ್ಕಲಿಗ ಮತದಾರರು ಇತರ ಜಾತಿಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ಮಿಶ್ರಣವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

2024ರ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಉಪಮುಖ್ಯಮಂತ್ರಿ ಡಿ. ಶಿವಕುಮಾರ್ ಅವರು ಬಿಜೆಪಿಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಹೊಂದಾಣಿಕೆ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಜೆಡಿಎಸ್‌ನೊಂದಿಗಿನ ನಿರಾಶೆಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸೇರಿಕೊಂಡರು. ವಿಶೇಷವೆಂದರೆ, ಜೆಡಿಎಸ್ ವರಿಷ್ಠ ಎಚ್‌ಡಿ ಇಬ್ಬರೂ ವಿಶೇಷ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ದೇವೇಗೌಡ ಹಾಗೂ ಅವರ ಪುತ್ರ ಎಚ್.ಡಿ. ಕುಮಾರಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಭಾವನಾತ್ಮಕ ಮನವಿಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಒಕ್ಕಲಿಗ ಸಮುದಾಯವನ್ನು ಒಲೈಸಲಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ದೇವೇಗೌಡರು ಪಕ್ಷದ ನಾಯಕರಾಗಿ ಇದು ಕೊನೆಯ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಾಗಿರಬಹುದು ಮತ್ತು ಕುಮಾರಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಅವರಿಗೆ ಮುಳುಗುತ್ತಿರುವ ಹಡಗನ್ನು ರಕ್ಷಿಸುವ ಅಂತಿಮ ಅವಕಾಶವಾಗಿರಬಹುದು. ಜೆಡಿ(ಎಸ್) ಕೂಡ "ಜಾತ್ಯತೀತ" ನಿರೂಪಣೆಗಳಿಂದ ಧೈರ್ಯದಿಂದ ದೂರ ಸರಿದಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಇನ್ನೂ ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸದ ಕೆಲವು ಒಕ್ಕಲಿಗ ಮತದಾರರು ಬಿಜೆಪಿ-ಜೆಡಿ (ಎಸ್) ಮೈತ್ರಿಗೆ ಮತ ಹಾಕಬಹುದು. ಕಳೆದ ವರ್ಷ ನಡೆದ ವಿಧಾನಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್, ಜೆಡಿಎಸ್ ಮತ್ತು ಬಿಜೆಪಿ ಮತದಾರರ ನಡುವೆ ಮೂರನೇ ಒಂದು ಭಾಗದಷ್ಟು ಭಿನ್ನಾಭಿಪ್ರಾಯ ಕಂಡುಬಂದಿದ್ದು, ಈ ಹಿಂದೆ ಒಕ್ಕಲಿಗ ಮತಗಳ ತಳಹದಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ ಮುನ್ನಡೆ ಸಾಧಿಸಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿದ್ದ

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ಅರಸು ಸಮುದಾಯಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿದ ಮಾಜಿ ಮುಖ್ಯಮಂತ್ರಿ ದೇವರಾಜ್ ಅರಸ್ ಅವರು ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರು, ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ವರ್ಗಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ದಲಿತರನ್ನು ಒಗ್ಗೂಡಿಸುವ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿದರು ಮತ್ತು 1970 ರ ದಶಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಹಿಂದ ಎಂಬ ಪದವನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸಿದರು - ಇದು ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರು (ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರು), ಹಿಂದುಳಿದವರು (ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ವರ್ಗಗಳು) ಮತ್ತು ದಲಿತರು (ದಲಿತರು). ಕುರುಬ ನಾಯಕರಾದ ಸಿದ್ದರಾಮಯ್ಯ ಅವರು 2013 ಮತ್ತು 2024 ರಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಮುಖ್ಯಮಂತ್ರಿಯಾಗುವುದರೊಂದಿಗೆ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ವ್ಯವಹಾರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಲ್ಲಿಕಾರ್ಜುನ ಖರ್ಗೆ ಅವರ ಸ್ಥಾನಮಾನವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುವುದರೊಂದಿಗೆ, ಅಹಿಂದ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಳೆಯ ಪಕ್ಷದಿಂದ ಪುನಶ್ಚೇತನಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. "ಇದಲ್ಲದೆ, ಜೆಡಿ (ಎಸ್) ಮತ್ತು ಬಿಜೆಪಿ ನಾಯಕರ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳು ನಿಜವಾಗಿ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡುತ್ತವೆಯೇ. ಸಿದ್ದರಾಮಯ್ಯ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದರೂ ಹಳೇ ಮೈಸೂರು ಭಾಗಕ್ಕೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಅವರ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಸೀಮಿತವಾಗಿಲ್ಲ. ಎರಡನೇ ಬಾರಿಗೆ ಮುಖ್ಯಮಂತ್ರಿಯಾಗಿ ಸೇವೆ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿದ ಸಿದ್ದರಾಮಯ್ಯನವರು ತಮ್ಮ ಉನ್ನತ ವಾಕ್ಯಾತುರ್ಯ, ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಗುರಿ ಮತ್ತು ನೇರದಾಳಿ, ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ವರ್ಗ ಎಂದು ಬಿಂಬಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ನಿರಾಕರಿಸಿದ ಕಾರಣದಿಂದ ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಜನನಾಯಕರಾಗಲು ಯಶಸ್ವಿಯಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ನಾಯಕ ಮತ್ತು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಗಮನಿಸಬೇಕಾದ ಅಂಶವೆಂದರೆ ದಲಿತರ ಮತಗಳಲ್ಲಿನ ವಿಭಜನೆಯಾಗಿದೆ, ದಲಿತ ಬಲವು ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಪಕ್ಷವನ್ನು ಬೆಂಬಲಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ಭಾವಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ದಲಿತ ಎಡಪಂಥೀಯರು ಬಿಜೆಪಿಯ ಪರವಾಗಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಅರ್ಥವಾಗುವಂತೆ, ಈ

ಊಹೆಯು ಯಾವಾಗಲೂ ನಿಜವೆಂದು ಸಾಬೀತುಪಡಿಸುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಳೆಯ ಪಕ್ಷದಿಂದ ಪುನಶ್ಚೇತನಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಎಸ್‌ಸಿಬಲ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ನಾಯಕರಲ್ಲಿ ಖರ್ಗೆ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸಚಿವರಾದ ಎಚ್.ಸಿ. ಮಹದೇವಪ್ಪ, ಜಿ. ಪರಮೇಶ್ವರ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಿಯಾಂಕ್ ಖರ್ಗೆ (ಮಲ್ಲಿಕಾರ್ಜುನ ಖರ್ಗೆ ಅವರ ಪುತ್ರ). ಮಾಜಿ ಸಂಪುಟ ಸಚಿವ ಕೆ.ಎಚ್. ಮುನಿಯಪ್ಪ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಜನಪ್ರಿಯ ಎಸ್ಸಿ ಎಡ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿ. 2014ರಲ್ಲಿ ಗೆದ್ದು 2019ರಲ್ಲಿ ಸೋತಿದ್ದ ಚಂದ್ರಪ್ಪ ಕೂಡ ಎಸ್‌ಸಿ ಎಡ ಸಮುದಾಯಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿದವರಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಪಕ್ಷದ ಚಿಕ್ಕಮಗಳೂರು ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಯ ಮೂಡಿಗೆರೆಯಿಂದ ಬಂದವರು. ಬಿಜೆಪಿಯ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿಯ ಮತದಾರರ ಮತ ವರ್ಗಾವಣೆ ಮತ್ತು ಉಳಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆಯ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಒಂದು ಗುಂಪಿನ ಮತದಾರರು ಕೇಸರಿ ಪಕ್ಷದ ಕಡೆಗೆ ಬದಲಾದರೆ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ಬಿಜೆಪಿ ಬೆಂಬಲವನ್ನು ಉಳಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದಾಗ್ಯೂ, ಒಕ್ಕಲಿಗ ಮತಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಅದು ಆಗದಿರಬಹುದು, ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ದೃಢವಾದ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಅನ್ನು ಈಗ "ಸ್ವರ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ಅಂಶ" ಎಂದು ನೋಡಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಒಬಿಸಿ ಕುರುಬ ಮತ್ತು ಈಡಿಗ ಮತದಾರರು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಸಿದ್ದರಾಮಯ್ಯ ಅವರ ನಾಯಕತ್ವದಿಂದಾಗಿ ಕುರುಬರು ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್‌ಗೆ ಬೆಂಬಲ ನೀಡುವ ಸಾಧ್ಯತೆಯಿದೆ ಆದರೆ ಲಿಂಗಾಯತೇತರ, ಒಕ್ಕಲಿಗೇತರ ಮತ್ತು ಕುರುಬೇತರ ಮತದಾರರು ಬಿಜೆಪಿಯತ್ತ ಬಲವು ತೋರುವ ಸಾಧ್ಯತೆಯಿದೆ, ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಪಕ್ಷವು ಒಕ್ಕಲಿಗರು ಮತ್ತು ಕುರುಬರ ಪಕ್ಷವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಗ್ರಂಥಸೂಚಿ

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ನಾಗರಾಜು ಜಿ ಎನ್.(2020). " ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅಸ್ವಶೃತೆ " ಉದಯ ಸಿ ಸೆಂಟರ್ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಪ್ರಥಮಮುದ್ರಣ.

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗದ ಮಾಹಿತಿ

ಅಂತರ್ಜಾಲ

ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಜ್ಜುಗೊಳಿಸುವಿಕೆ: ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ನೆಲೆಗಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆ

ಸಂಪತ್ ಶಾನಪ್ಪ ಲಮಾಣಿ

ಸಂಶೋಧನಾ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿ, ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ವಿಭಾಗ

ರಾಣಿ ಚನ್ನಮ್ಮ ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ, ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ

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ಪ್ರೊ. ಕಮಲಾಕ್ಷಿ ಜಿ ತಡಸದ

ಪ್ರಾಧ್ಯಾಪಕರು ಮತ್ತು ಮುಖ್ಯಸ್ಥರು

ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ವಿಭಾಗ

ರಾಣಿ ಚನ್ನಮ್ಮ ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ, ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ

Abstract

ಈ ಸಂಶೋಧನಾ ಪ್ರಬಂಧವು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿನ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ರೋಢೀಕರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ನಡುವಿನ ಸಂಬಂಧವನ್ನು ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಭಾರತದ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಹೊಂದಿದ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಾಗಿದ್ದರೂ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ಪ್ರಗತಿಯಿಂದ ಸಮಾನವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನ ಪಡೆಯುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ. ಈ ಲೇಖನವು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ-ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ವಿವಿಧ ಹಂತಗಳನ್ನು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸುವ ಗುರಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ, ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ತಾರತಮ್ಯವನ್ನು ಅನುಭವಿಸಲು ಕಾರಣವಾಗುವ ಅಂಶಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ತಾರತಮ್ಯವನ್ನು ನಿವಾರಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ರೋಢೀಕರಣದ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಕಡಿಮೆ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಸೂಚ್ಯಂಕಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ಬಲವಾದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಇಚ್ಛಾಶಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರದರ್ಶಿಸಬೇಕು ಎಂದು ಫಲಿತಾಂಶಗಳು ತೋರಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಬಂಡವಾಳ ಕೇಂದ್ರಿತ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಿಸುವ ಬದಲು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಸೇರಿದಂತೆ ವಿವಿಧ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯನ್ನು ಬೆಂಬಲಿಸುವ ನೀತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಪಡಿಸಬೇಕು ಎಂದು ಈ ಲೇಖನವಾದಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಧ್ವನಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿ ಕೇಳಿಬರುತ್ತಿರುವ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜನರಲ್ಲಿ ಅಂಚಿನಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಭಾವನೆ, ಈ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಯು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಇಚ್ಛಾಶಕ್ತಿಯ ನಡುವಿನ ಸಂಕೀರ್ಣವಾದ ಪರಸ್ಪರ ಕ್ರಿಯೆಯನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಕೊಡುಗೆ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಸಮಾನವಾದ ಆಡಳಿತ ಮತ್ತು ನೀತಿ ಮಧ್ಯಸ್ಥಿಕೆಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸುವ ಒಳನೋಟಗಳನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

Key Words: ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮಾನತೆ, ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮತೋಲನ, ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಜ್ಜುಗೊಳಿಸುವಿಕೆ

ಪೀಠಿಕೆ:

ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಭಾರತದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ರಾಜ್ಯವಾದ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವು ತನ್ನ ವಿವಿಧ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಗಮನಾರ್ಹವಾದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ-ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಗಳಿಂದ ಗುರುತಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿದೆ. ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ, ಭೌಗೋಳಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಅಂಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಬೇರೂರಿರುವ ಈ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಗಳು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮಾದರಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ರೋಢೀಕರಣ ಎರಡನ್ನೂ ರೂಪಿಸಿವೆ. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿನ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ರೋಢೀಕರಣದ ನಡುವಿನ ಸಂಬಂಧವನ್ನು ಅನ್ವೇಷಿಸುವ ಗುರಿಯನ್ನು ಈ ಪತ್ರಿಕೆ ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ರಾಜ್ಯವನ್ನು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ನಾಲ್ಕು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಾಗಿ ವಿಂಗಡಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ: ಕರಾವಳಿ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ, ಮಲೆನಾಡು ಪ್ರದೇಶ, ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ, ಮತ್ತು ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ. ಈ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ-ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಗುಣಲಕ್ಷಣಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರದರ್ಶಿಸುತ್ತವೆ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಪಥಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ತಮ್ಮ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಭಾವಿಸುತ್ತವೆ.

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯು ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕವಾಗಿ ವಸಾಹತುಶಾಹಿ ನೀತಿಗಳು, ಮೈಸೂರಿನ ರಾಜಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಆಡಳಿತ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯಾನಂತರದ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳಿಂದ ಪ್ರಭಾವಿತವಾಗಿದೆ. ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುವ ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ರಾಜ್ಯವು ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ, ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಸೇವೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಹೂಡಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಿತು, ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯದ ನಂತರ ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ತ್ವರಿತ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಅಡಿಪಾಯ ಹಾಕಿತು. ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ವ್ಯತಿರಿಕ್ತವಾಗಿ, ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕವಾಗಿ ನಿಜಾಮರ ಹೈದರಾಬಾದ್ ಮತ್ತು ಬಾಂಬೆ ಪ್ರೆಸಿಡೆನ್ಸಿಯ ಭಾಗವಾದ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವು ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅಸಮರ್ಪಕ ಹೂಡಿಕೆಯಿಂದಾಗಿ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದಿದೆ. ಈ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ವಿಭಜನೆಯು ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ದರಗಳಂತಹ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ-ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಸೂಚಕಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ದೀರ್ಘಾವಧಿಯ ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಸೇವೆಗಳು, ಉದ್ಯೋಗಾವಕಾಶಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಆದಾಯ ಮಟ್ಟಗಳು, ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ವಿವಿಧ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಬಹಳಷ್ಟು ವೈರುಧ್ಯತೆಯಿಂದ ಕೂಡಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಕಂಡುಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣಗಳು:

1. ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ನಿರ್ಲಕ್ಷ್ಯ

ಕಲ್ಯಾಣ- ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ, ಪ್ರದೇಶ (ಹಿಂದೆ ಹೈದರಾಬಾದ್- ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ), ಮತ್ತು ಕಿತ್ತೂರು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ, (ಹಿಂದೆ ಮುಂಬೈ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ), ಹಿಂದಿನ ನಿಜಾಮರ ಆಳ್ವಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಭಾಗಗಳು, ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ವಿಷಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕವಾಗಿ ನಿರ್ಲಕ್ಷಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟವು. ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯಾನಂತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ರಾಜ್ಯ ರಚನೆಯಾದಾಗ ಹಳೆಯ ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿದ್ದ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ಉತ್ತಮ ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಆಡಳಿತವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದವು. ಆದಾಗ್ಯೂ, ಉತ್ತರದ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ಕೈಗಾರಿಕಾ ಮತ್ತು ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಹೂಡಿಕೆಗಳ ಕೊರತೆಯಿಂದ ಬಳಲುತ್ತಿದ್ದವು, ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ನಿಧಾನಗತಿಯ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ಹಾದಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಇರಿಸಿದವು.

2. ಭೌಗೋಳಿಕ ಅಂಶಗಳು

ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವು ಕರಾವಳಿ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಕೇಂದ್ರವಾಗಿರುವ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು, ಮೈಸೂರು ಮತ್ತು ಮಂಗಳೂರಿನಂತಹ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ನಗರ ಕೇಂದ್ರಗಳಿಗೆ ಪ್ರವೇಶದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಅನುಕೂಲಕರವಾದ ಭೌಗೋಳಿಕ ಸೆಟ್ಟಿಂಗ್ ಅನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ಉತ್ತಮ ನೈಸರ್ಗಿಕ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳು, ಫಲವತ್ತಾದ ಭೂಮಿ ಮತ್ತು ವ್ಯಾಪಾರ ಮಾರ್ಗಗಳ ಸಾಮೀಪ್ಯದಿಂದ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನ ಪಡೆಯುತ್ತವೆ. ಮತ್ತೊಂದೆಡೆ, ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ (ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ರಾಯಚೂರು, ಯಾದಗಿರಿ ಮತ್ತು ಕೊಪ್ಪಳದಂತಹ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು) ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿ ಶುಷ್ಕ ಮತ್ತು ಬರಪೀಡಿತವಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಕೃಷಿ ಉತ್ಪಾದಕತೆಯು ಮಳೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಅವಲಂಬಿತವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದು ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಕೃಷಿ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆ ಮತ್ತು ಕೈಗಾರಿಕಾ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಎರಡನ್ನೂ ಅಡ್ಡಿಪಡಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

3. ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಕೈಗಾರಿಕಾ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ

ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಭಾರತದ ಐಟಿ ರಾಜಧಾನಿಯಾಗಿ ಹೊರಹೊಮ್ಮಿದೆ, ಜಗತ್ತಿನಾದ್ಯಂತ ಬೃಹತ್ ಹೂಡಿಕೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಮಾನವ ಬಂಡವಾಳವನ್ನು ಆಕರ್ಷಿಸುತ್ತಿದೆ. ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಕೈಗಾರಿಕೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ವ್ಯವಹಾರಗಳ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವು ಆ ಪ್ರದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ತ್ವರಿತ ನಗರೀಕರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ವ್ಯತಿರಿಕ್ತವಾಗಿ, ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವು ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕವಾಗಿ ಕೃಷಿಪ್ರಧಾನವಾಗಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅದೇ ಮಟ್ಟದ ಕೈಗಾರಿಕೀಕರಣವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿಲ್ಲ. ಉತ್ತರದಲ್ಲಿ ಕೈಗಾರಿಕೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಉತ್ತೇಜನ ನೀಡುವ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳು ನಡೆದಿವೆ, ಆದರೆ ಅವು ದಕ್ಷಿಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಯಶಸ್ವಿಯಾದಷ್ಟು ವ್ಯಾಪಕವಾಗಿಲ್ಲ.

4. ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಗಳು

ಸಾರಿಗೆ (ರೈಲ್ವೆ, ಹೆದ್ದಾರಿಗಳು, ವಿಮಾನ ನಿಲ್ದಾಣಗಳು), ಶಕ್ತಿ ಮತ್ತು ದೂರಸಂಪರ್ಕ ಸೇರಿದಂತೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ಭೌತಿಕ ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯದಿಂದ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ, ಪ್ರಯೋಜನ ಪಡೆಯುತ್ತದೆ. ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಅಂತಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ವಿಮಾನ ನಿಲ್ದಾಣಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಮೆಟ್ರೋ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಸೇರಿದಂತೆ ವಿಶ್ವದರ್ಜೆಯ ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಹೋಲಿಸಿದರೆ, ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯವು ಕಳಪೆ ರಸ್ತೆ ಸಂಪರ್ಕ ಸೀಮಿತ ಕೈಗಾರಿಕಾ ಕಾರಿಡಾರ್‌ಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅಸಮರ್ಪಕ ನಗರ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಹೊಂದಿಲ್ಲ. ಇದು ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೈಗಾರಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಹೊಂದಲು ಕಷ್ಟಕರವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ.

5. ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳು

ಗುಣಮಟ್ಟದ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಮತ್ತು ಆರೋಗ್ಯದ ಲಭ್ಯತೆಯು ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಕಡೆಗೆ ತಿರುಗಿದೆ. ರಾಜ್ಯದ ರಾಜಧಾನಿ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಮತ್ತು ಇತರ ದಕ್ಷಿಣದ ನಗರಗಳು ಹಲವಾರು ಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠಿತ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು, ಕಾಲೇಜುಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಆಯೋಜಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ವ್ಯತಿರಿಕ್ತವಾಗಿ, ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವು ಶಾಲೆಗಳು, ಕಾಲೇಜುಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ವೈದ್ಯಕೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ಕೊರತೆಯಂತಹ ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತಿದೆ, ಇದರ ಪರಿಣಾಮವಾಗಿ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ದರಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಕಳಪೆ ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಫಲಿತಾಂಶಗಳು. ಈ ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ವಿಭಾಗವು ಉತ್ತರದ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾನವ ಬಂಡವಾಳದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯನ್ನು ಮಿತಿಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

6. ಕೃಷಿ ಅವಲಂಬನೆ

ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜನಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಭಾಗವು ಕೃಷಿಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಅವಲಂಬಿತವಾಗಿದೆ, ಇದು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಅನಿಯಮಿತ ಮಾನ್ಯೂನ್ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ನೀರಾವರಿ ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯಗಳಿಂದ ಪ್ರಭಾವಿತವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವು ಕಾವೇರಿ ನದಿ ಜಲಾನಯನ ಪ್ರದೇಶದಂತಹ ನೀರಾವರಿ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳಿಂದ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನ ಪಡೆದಿದ್ದರೆ, ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಕೃಷಿ ಮತ್ತು ತುಂಗಭದ್ರಾ ಜಲಾನಯನ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ನೀರಿನ ಕೊರತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಬರಗಾಲವನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಈ ಕೃಷಿ ದುರ್ಬಲತೆಯು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಆದಾಯದ ಮಟ್ಟಗಳು, ಬಡತನ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತರದಲ್ಲಿ ನಿಧಾನವಾದ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಗೆ ಕೊಡುಗೆ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ.

7. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಅಂಚು

ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದರೂ, ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಹೊಂದಿದ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಭಾಗಕ್ಕೆ ಹೋಲಿಸಿದರೆ ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶವು ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕವಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಅಂಚಿನಲ್ಲಿದೆ. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನಾಯಕತ್ವ ಮತ್ತು ನಿರ್ಧಾರ ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆಯು ದಕ್ಷಿಣದ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ, ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರಿನ ಸುತ್ತಮುತ್ತ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತವಾಗಿದೆ, ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಕಾಳಜಿಗಳಿಗೆ ತುಲನಾತ್ಮಕವಾಗಿ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಗಮನವನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದು ಉತ್ತರದ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಸ್ವಾಯತ್ತತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲ ಹಂಚಿಕೆಗಾಗಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚುತ್ತಿರುವ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ.

8. ನಗರೀಕರಣ ಮತ್ತು ವಲಸೆಯ ಮಾದರಿಗಳು

ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ, ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ತ್ವರಿತ ನಗರೀಕರಣವು ಉತ್ತರದ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಿಂದ ದಕ್ಷಿಣದ ನಗರಗಳಿಗೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ಉದ್ಯೋಗಾವಕಾಶಗಳ ಹುಡುಕಾಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ ಆಂತರಿಕ ವಲಸೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ವಲಸೆಯ ಮಾದರಿಯು ದಕ್ಷಿಣದ ನಗರ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಪತ್ತು, ಸೇವೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ, ಆದರೆ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಮತ್ತು ಕಡಿಮೆ ನಗರೀಕರಣಗೊಂಡ ಉತ್ತರದ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ವಿಷಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದಿವೆ.

ಕೇಸ್ ಸ್ಟಡಿ:

ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ-ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಸೂಚಕಗಳ ಪರಿಮಾಣಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆಯು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಗಳನ್ನು ಎತ್ತಿ ತೋರಿಸಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ, ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಹೊಂದಿದ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು (ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು, ಮೈಸೂರು ನಂತಹ) ಮತ್ತು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಹೊಂದಿದ ಉತ್ತರ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು (ಕಲಬುರಗಿ, ರಾಯಚೂರು, ಬೀದರ್ ಮತ್ತು ಕೊಪ್ಪಳ). ತಲಾ ಆದಾಯ, ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ದರಗಳು, ಬಡತನ ಮಟ್ಟಗಳು, ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಪ್ರವೇಶ, ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಫಲಿತಾಂಶಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಉದ್ಯೋಗದ ಮಾದರಿಗಳಂತಹ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ-ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಸೂಚಕಗಳನ್ನು ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಈ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಗಳನ್ನು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸಬಹುದು. ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮತೋಲನವನ್ನು ಪ್ರದರ್ಶಿಸಲು ಈ ಸೂಚಕಗಳ ಪರಿಮಾಣಾತ್ಮಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಮಾಪನವನ್ನು ಕೆಳಗೆ ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ:

ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ**1. ತಲಾ ಆದಾಯ ಸೂಚ್ಯಂಕ:**

ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ: ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು, ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ನಗರ ಮತ್ತು ಮೈಸೂರು, ಕೈಗಾರಿಕಾ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ, ಐಟಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತಮ ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯದಿಂದಾಗಿ ಗಣನೀಯವಾಗಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ತಲಾ ಆದಾಯವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿವೆ. ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ನಗರ (0.77), ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕನ್ನಡ (0.72), ಚಿಕ್ಕಮಗಳೂರು(0.67), ಉಡುಪಿ(0.68), ಕೊಡಗು(0.61), ಮಂಡ್ಯ(0.60), ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ (0.62), ರಾಮನಗರ(0.61), ಕೋಲಾರ(0.56) ಮತ್ತು ಶಿವಮೊಗ್ಗ (0.62) ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಮೊದಲ ಹತ್ತು ಸ್ಥಾನದಲ್ಲಿದ್ದು, ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಯಾವ ಒಂದು ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಸ್ಥಾನವನ್ನು ಪಡೆದಿಲ್ಲ. ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ವ್ಯತಿರಿಕ್ತವಾಗಿ, ಉತ್ತರದ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಕಡಿಮೆ ತಲಾ ಆದಾಯದ ಸೂಚ್ಯಂಕವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದು. ಕೊನೆಯ ಹತ್ತು ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಏಳು ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿವೆ. ಯಾದಗಿರಿ(0.53), ಕಲಬುರಗಿ(0.51), ರಾಯಚೂರು(0.53), ಹಾವೇರಿ(0.53), ಕೊಪ್ಪಳ(0.52), ವಿಜಯಪುರ(0.53),ಬೀದರ್(0.52) ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಸರಾಸರಿ ತಲಾದಾಯ ಸೂಚ್ಯಂಕವು 0.634 ಆಗಿದೆ.

2. ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದ ಸೂಚ್ಯಂಕ:

ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ನಗರ: 87.67% ಮೈಸೂರು: 82.81% ಸಾಕ್ಷರತಾ ಪ್ರಮಾಣವನ್ನು ದಾಖಲಿಸಿದ್ದರೆ,ಯಾದಗಿರಿ: 51.83% ರಾಯಚೂರು: 59.56% ಅತಿ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತಾ ಪ್ರಮಾಣವನ್ನು ದಾಖಲಿಸಿವೆ. ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದ ಸೂಚ್ಯಂಕವನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿದಾಗ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು(0.67) ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕನ್ನಡ(0.59) ಚಿಕ್ಕಮಗಳೂರು(0.576) ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದರೆ, ಯಾದಗಿರಿ (0.382), ಕಲಬುರಗಿ(0.42) ರಾಯಚೂರು(0.448) ಹಾವೇರಿ (0.446)ಹೊಂದಿವೆ. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಸರಾಸರಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದ ಸೂಚ್ಯಂಕವು 0.555 ಆಗಿದೆ.

3. ಬಡತನ ಮತ್ತು ಮಾನವ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಸೂಚ್ಯಂಕ (HDI)

ಬಡತನ ದರವನ್ನು ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ನಗರ (6.5%) ಮೈಸೂರು(9.8%) ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದರೆ, ಕಲಬುರಗಿ 28.7% ರಾಯಚೂರು 30.1% ಹೊಂದಿವೆ. ಮಾನವ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಸೂಚ್ಯಂಕ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ನಗರ: 0.738 (ಅತಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚು) ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕನ್ನಡ 0.687 (ಹೆಚ್ಚು) ಕಲಬುರಗಿ 53.9(ಕಡಿಮೆ) ಯಾದಗಿರಿ 0. 53.8 (ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಕಡಿಮೆ) ಹೊಂದಿವೆ. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಸರಾಸರಿ ಮಾನವ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಸೂಚ್ಯಂಕವು 0.644 ಆಗಿದೆ.

4. ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಸೂಚಕಗಳು

ಶಿಶು ಮರಣ ಪ್ರಮಾಣ :ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ನಗರ: ಪ್ರತಿ 1000 ಜನನಗಳಿಗೆ 15 ಸಾವುಗಳು,ಮೈಸೂರು 1000 ಜನನಗಳಿಗೆ 20 ಸಾವುಗಳು ಕಲಬುರಗಿ ಪ್ರತಿ 1000 ಜನನಗಳಿಗೆ 37 ಸಾವು ರಾಯಚೂರು ಪ್ರತಿ 1000 ಜನನಗಳಿಗೆ 42 ಸಾವು ದಾಖಲಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿವೆ.

ತಾಯಿಯ ಮರಣ ಪ್ರಮಾಣವು ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ: 100000 ಜೀವಂತ ಜನನಗಳಿಗೆ 108 ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ: 100000 ಜೀವಂತ ಜನನಗಳಿಗೆ 178 ಪ್ರಮಾಣವನ್ನು ದಾಖಲಿಸಿದೆ.

ಯಾದಗಿರಿ ಮತ್ತು ಕೊಪ್ಪಳದಂತಹ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯಗಳ ಕೊರತೆಯಿದೆ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರಿನಂತಹ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೋಲಿಸಿದರೆ ತಲಾ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಆಸ್ಪತ್ರೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕ ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಕೇಂದ್ರಗಳು (PHC) ಇವೆ.

ಅಸಮರ್ಪಕ ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಸೇವೆಗಳು, ತಾಯಿಯ ಮತ್ತು ಮಕ್ಕಳ ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಫಲಿತಾಂಶಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಗುಣಮಟ್ಟದ ವೈದ್ಯಕೀಯ ಆರೈಕೆಗೆ ಸೀಮಿತ ಪ್ರವೇಶವನ್ನು ಸೂಚಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

5. ಕೃಷಿ ಅವಲಂಬನೆ ಮತ್ತು ನೀರಾವರಿ

ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಪ್ರಮಾಣದ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕರು ಕೃಷಿಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಅವಲಂಬಿತರಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಕಲಬುರಗಿ 65% ರಾಯಚೂರು ಶೇ.68 ಯಾದಗಿರಿ ಶೇ.75 ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕರು ಕೃಷಿಯನ್ನೇ ಅವಲಂಬಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ (ಮಂಡ್ಯ) 80% ಕೃಷಿಯೋಗ್ಯ ಭೂಮಿ ನೀರಾವರಿ (ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕವಾಗಿ ಕಾವೇರಿ ನದಿ ನೀರಾವರಿ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಿಂದಾಗಿ)ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ (ಕಲಬುರಗಿ): 40% ಕೃಷಿಯೋಗ್ಯ ಭೂಮಿ ನೀರಾವರಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ.

ಉತ್ತರದ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೃಷಿಯ ಮೇಲಿನ ಅವಲಂಬನೆಯು ದಕ್ಷಿಣಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನದಾಗಿದೆ, ಅಲ್ಲಿ ಉದ್ಯಮ ಮತ್ತು ಸೇವೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ವೈವಿಧ್ಯತೆ ಇದೆ. ಮೇಲಾಗಿ ಉತ್ತರ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ನೀರಾವರಿ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದು, ಕೃಷಿ ಮೇಲ್ದಂಡೆ ಯೋಜನೆಯಂತಹ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು ವಿಳಂಬವನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಇದು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಕೃಷಿ ಉತ್ಪಾದಕತೆಗೆ ಕೊಡುಗೆ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಬರಗಾಲದ ದುರ್ಬಲತೆಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

6. ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಮೂಲ ಸೇವೆಗಳು

ರಸ್ತೆ ಸಂಪರ್ಕ :

ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ, (ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು): 90% ಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಹಳ್ಳಿಗಳು ಸುಸಜ್ಜಿತ ರಸ್ತೆಗಳಿಂದ ಸಂಪರ್ಕ ಹೊಂದಿವೆ. ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ (ಯಾದಗಿರಿ): ಸುಸಜ್ಜಿತ ರಸ್ತೆಗಳಿಂದ ಸಂಪರ್ಕ ಹೊಂದಿದ 50% ಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಹಳ್ಳಿಗಳು ಹೊಂದಿವೆ.

ವಿದ್ಯುದೀಕರಣ

ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ (ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು): 99% ವಿದ್ಯುದೀಕರಣ ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದರೆ, ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ (ರಾಯಚೂರು, ಕಲಬುರಗಿ): 75-80% ವಿದ್ಯುದೀಕರಣ ಹೊಂದಿವೆ.

ಕುಡಿಯುವ ನೀರಿಗೆ ಪ್ರವೇಶ:

ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ನಗರ 93% ಕುಟುಂಬಗಳು ಪೈಪ್ ಮೂಲಕ ಕುಡಿಯುವ ನೀರಿನ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯ ವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿವೆ.ಯಾದಗಿರಿ ಶೇ.40ರಷ್ಟು ಕುಟುಂಬಗಳಿಗೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಪೈಪ್‌ಲೈನ್ ಮೂಲಕ ಕುಡಿಯುವ ನೀರು ಲಭ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ.

ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ರಸ್ತೆ ಸಂಪರ್ಕ, ವಿದ್ಯುತ್, ಮತ್ತು ಕುಡಿಯುವ ನೀರಿನ ಪ್ರವೇಶ ಸೇರಿದಂತೆ ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಮುಂದುವರಿದಿದೆ. ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ, ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು, ಇನ್ನೂ ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ಹೋರಾಡುತ್ತಿವೆ ಇದು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ಜೀವನದ ಗುಣಮಟ್ಟದ ಗುಣಮಟ್ಟಕ್ಕೆ ಅಡ್ಡಿಪಡಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

7.ನಗರೀಕರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಉದ್ಯೋಗ ಅವಕಾಶಗಳು

ನಗರೀಕರಣ ದರ:

ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ನಗರ 90.94% ಮೈಸೂರು 47.62% ರಾಯಚೂರು 25.75% ಯಾದಗಿರಿ 20.30% ಹೊಂದಿವೆ.

ದಕ್ಷಿಣಕ್ಕೆ ಹೋಲಿಸಿದರೆ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವು ಕಡಿಮೆ ನಗರೀಕರಣಗೊಂಡಿದೆ, ಕೃಷಿಯೇತರ ಉದ್ಯೋಗಗಳಿಗೆ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಅವಕಾಶಗಳಿವೆ. ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರುದ್ಯೋಗವೂ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿದ್ದು, ಕೆಲಸಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಅಥವಾ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಹೊರಗಿನ ನಗರಗಳಿಗೆ ವಲಸೆ ಹೋಗುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯು ರಾಜಧಾನಿ-ಕೇಂದ್ರಿತ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಯಾಗಿದ್ದು ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು, ರಾಜ್ಯ ರಾಜಧಾನಿ ಮತ್ತು ಜಾಗತಿಕ ಐಟಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರವಾಗಿದ್ದು, ತ್ವರಿತ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆ, ನಗರೀಕರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯನ್ನು ಅನುಭವಿಸಿದೆ, ಉತ್ತರದ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ತುಲನಾತ್ಮಕವಾಗಿ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದಿವೆ. ಈ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಯ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಯು ರಾಜ್ಯದಾದ್ಯಂತ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ, ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳು, ಹೂಡಿಕೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅವಕಾಶಗಳು ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಮತ್ತು ಸುತ್ತಮುತ್ತ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತವಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವನ್ನು ಹಿಂದುಳಿಯಲು ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿವೆ

ರಾಜ್ಯದ ರಾಜಧಾನಿ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಕೇಂದ್ರವಾಗಿ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಅಸಮಾನವಾದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಗಮನ ಮತ್ತು ಆಡಳಿತ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯುತ್ತದೆ. ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ನೀತಿಗಳು, ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಉಪಕ್ರಮಗಳು ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರಿನ ನಗರ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಗೆ ಅನುಕೂಲವಾಗುವಂತೆ ವಿನ್ಯಾಸಗೊಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ, ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಅಗತ್ಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಆದ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಸಮಾನ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲ ಹಂಚಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ನಿಧಿಗಳ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವು ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ ನಿರ್ಲಕ್ಷ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಒಳಗಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಭಾವಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯವು ಬೆಂಗಳೂರಿನ ಪ್ರಾಬಲ್ಯದಿಂದ ಗಮನವನ್ನು ಬೇರೆಡೆಗೆ ತಿರುಗಿಸಲು ಹೆಣಗಾಡುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗೆ, ಹೈದರಾಬಾದ್-ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪ್ರದೇಶಕ್ಕೆ ಆರ್ಟಿಎಲ್ 371 (ಜೆ) ಅಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಒದಗಿಸಲಾದ ಸಾಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ ಸುರಕ್ಷತೆಗಳ ಹೊರತಾಗಿಯೂ, ವಿಳಂಬವಾದ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಅಸಮರ್ಪಕ ಧನಸಹಾಯದಿಂದಾಗಿ ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶವು ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಇನ್ನೂ ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿಲ್ಲ. ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ನೀತಿಗಳು ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಮತ್ತು ಸುತ್ತಮುತ್ತಲಿನ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಿಗೆ ಅಸಮಾನವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನವನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತವೆ.

ಅಸಮಾನತೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಿವಾರಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಜ್ಜುಗೊಳಿಸುವಿಕೆಯ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳು:

1. ವಿಶೇಷ ಸ್ಥಾನಮಾನಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ವಕಾಲತ್ತು (ಆರ್ಟಿಎಲ್ 371(ಜೆ))

ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ರೋಢೀಕರಣದ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಮಹತ್ವದ ಫಲಿತಾಂಶವೆಂದರೆ ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ 371(ಜೆ)ವಿಧಿ ಅಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಶೇಷ ಸ್ಥಾನಮಾನಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಯಶಸ್ವಿ ಅಭಿಯಾನವಾಗಿದೆ. 2013 ರಲ್ಲಿ ನೀಡಲಾದ ಈ ನಿಬಂಧನೆಯು ಕಲ್ಯಾಣ-ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪ್ರದೇಶಕ್ಕೆ (ಹಿಂದಿನ ಹೈದರಾಬಾದ್-ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ) ಅನ್ವಯಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ನಿವಾಸಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಉದ್ಯೋಗಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೋಟಾ. ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ವಿಶೇಷ ನಿಧಿಗಳು. ಕೆಲವು ವಲಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಉದ್ಯೋಗದ ಆದ್ಯತೆ ನೀಡಿದೆ. ಈ ವಿಶೇಷ ಸ್ಥಾನಮಾನವು ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕಕ್ಕೆ ಹೋಲಿಸಿದರೆ ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ನಿರ್ಲಕ್ಷ್ಯವನ್ನು ಎತ್ತಿ ಹಿಡಿದ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ನಾಯಕರು ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಘಟನೆಗಳ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವಕಾಲತ್ತಿನ ಫಲಿತಾಂಶವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಜನಾಂದೋಲನವು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಮತ್ತು ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ರಕ್ಷಣೆಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಗಮನವನ್ನು ನೀಡಿತು.

2. ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಚಳುವಳಿಗಳು

ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನಾಯಕರು ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮತೋಲನದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯ ಸುತ್ತ ಸಜ್ಜುಗೊಳಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ, ತಮ್ಮ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಹೂಡಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕೋರಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಕಲಬುರಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಬೀದರ್‌ನಂತಹ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳ ನಾಯಕರು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು,

ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ಅಗತ್ಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಕೆಲವು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ರಾಜ್ಯ ವಿಭಜನೆಯ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಸಹ ಎತ್ತಿದ್ದು, ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತ ಗಮನವನ್ನು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ರಾಜ್ಯವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾಪಿಸಿವೆ. ಹೊಸ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯು ವ್ಯಾಪಕವಾದ ಎಳೆತವನ್ನು ಪಡೆದಿದ್ದರೂ, ಇದು ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಹಣ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳನ್ನು ನಿಯೋಜಿಸಲು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಒತ್ತಡವನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸಿದೆ.

3.. ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಭಾವ

ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಜ್ಜುಗೊಳಿಸುವಿಕೆಯು ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಡೈನಾಮಿಕ್ಸ್ ಅನ್ನು ಗಣನೀಯವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಭಾವಿಸಿದೆ. ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್, ಭಾರತೀಯ ಜನತಾ ಪಕ್ಷ (ಬಿಜೆಪಿ), ಮತ್ತು ಜನತಾ ದಳ (ಜಾತ್ಯತೀತ) ನಂತರ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಬೆಂಬಲವನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಹೂಡಿಕೆ ಮಾಡುವ ಭರವಸೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಿವೆ. ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆ ಹೊಂದಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಣಾಳಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಸ್ತೆ, ನೀರಾವರಿ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು, ಕೈಗಾರಿಕಾ ಕಾರಿಡಾರ್‌ಗಳಂತಹ ಪ್ರದೇಶಾಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸೇರಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿವೆ. ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ, ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನಾಯಕರು ಉತ್ತರ ಮತ್ತು ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ನಡುವಿನ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಯನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡುವ ಅಗತ್ಯವನ್ನು ಒತ್ತಿಹೇಳುತ್ತಾರೆ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳ ಸಮಾನ ಹಂಚಿಕೆಗೆ ಒತ್ತಾಯಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.

4. ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮಂಡಳಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು

ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಜ್ಜುಗೊಳಿಸುವಿಕೆಯು ಕಲ್ಯಾಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪ್ರದೇಶ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮಂಡಳಿ ಯಂತಹ ವಿಶೇಷ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ರಚನೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ, ಇದು ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳನ್ನು ವೇಗಗೊಳಿಸಲು, ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ, ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ರಕ್ಷಣೆ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಕೈಗಾರಿಕೀಕರಣವನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವ ಕಾರ್ಯವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳು ಬರಪೀಡಿತ ಉತ್ತರದ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೃಷಿ ಉತ್ಪಾದಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಸುಧಾರಿಸುವ ಗುರಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಅತಿ ದೊಡ್ಡ ನೀರಾವರಿ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಾದ ಮೇಲಿನ ಕೃಷ್ಣಾ ನೀರಾವರಿ ಯೋಜನೆಯನ್ನು ಸಹ ತಂದಿವೆ. ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಕೃಷಿ ಆರ್ಥಿಕತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಜೀವನೋಪಾಯವನ್ನು ಸುಧಾರಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಯನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡಲು ಈ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು ಅತ್ಯಗತ್ಯ.

5. ಬರ ಮತ್ತು ಕೃಷಿ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸುವುದು

ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವು ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಬರಗಾಲಕ್ಕೆ ತುತ್ತಾಗಿದೆ, ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ರೋಢೀಕರಣವು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ನೀರಾವರಿ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು, ಜಲಾನಯನ ನಿರ್ವಹಣೆ ಮತ್ತು ಕೃಷಿ ಉತ್ಪಾದಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಸುಧಾರಿಸಲು ಬರ-ಪರಿಹಾರ ಕ್ರಮಗಳಿಗೆ ಒತ್ತಾಯಿಸಿದೆ. ಜನಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯ ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿರುವ ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ರೈತರನ್ನು ಬೆಂಬಲಿಸಲು ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ನಾಯಕರು ಪರಿಹಾರ ಪ್ಯಾಕೇಜ್‌ಗಳು, ಸಬ್ಸಿಡಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯಗಳಿಗಾಗಿ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಒತ್ತಡ ಹೇರಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

6. ತಳಮಟ್ಟದ ಸಜ್ಜುಗೊಳಿಸುವಿಕೆ

ಔಪಚಾರಿಕ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವಕಾಲತ್ತುಗಳ ಜೊತೆಗೆ, ತಳಮಟ್ಟದ ಚಳುವಳಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ದುರವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಎತ್ತಿ ತೋರಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸಿವೆ. ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಯುವಕರಿಗೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ರಸ್ತೆಗಳು, ಶಾಲೆಗಳು, ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಉದ್ಯೋಗಾವಕಾಶಗಳಿಗಾಗಿ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಗುಂಪುಗಳು ಪ್ರತಿಭಟನೆಗಳು, ಮೆರವಣಿಗೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿಯಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಆಯೋಜಿಸಿವೆ. ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನಾಯಕರಿಂದ ಬೆಂಬಲಿತವಾದ ಈ

ಚಳುವಳಿಗಳು, ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳು ರಾಜ್ಯದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕಾರ್ಯಸೂಚಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಉಳಿಯುವುದನ್ನು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರವಹಿಸಿವೆ.

7. ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಕೈಗಾರಿಕೀಕರಣ ಪುಶ್

ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಜ್ಜುಗೊಳಿಸುವಿಕೆಯು ಉತ್ತರದ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೈಗಾರಿಕೀಕರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳಿಗೆ ತಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ. ಸುವರ್ಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಕಾರಿಡಾರ್‌ನಂತಹ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಉಪಕ್ರಮಗಳು ರಸ್ತೆ ಸಂಪರ್ಕವನ್ನು ಸುಧಾರಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಕೈಗಾರಿಕಾ ಕೇಂದ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ರಚಿಸುವತ್ತ ಗಮನಹರಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಈ ಮೂಲಸೌಕರ್ಯ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳು ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶಕ್ಕೆ ಕೈಗಾರಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಆಕರ್ಷಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಆದಾಯದ ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕ ಮೂಲವಾಗಿ ಕೃಷಿಯ ಮೇಲಿನ ಅವಲಂಬನೆಯನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡುವ ಗುರಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿವೆ.

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ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕತೆಯ ಬೇಡಿಕೆ: ಸಾಧ್ಯತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸವಾಲುಗಳು

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ಸಾರಾಂಶ

ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ನಂತರ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿದ್ದ ನೂರಾರು ದೇಶೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಥಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಭಾರತದ ಒಕ್ಕೂಟದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸೇರಿಸಲು ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ನೀಡಿ ನಿರೂಪಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕೈಗೊಂಡು ಸರ್ವಾರ್ ವಲ್ಲಭ ಭಾಯ್ ಪಟೇಲರವರ ನೇತೃತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಟೇಟ್ಸ್ ಮಿನಿಸ್ಟ್ರಿಯನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಆದರಂತೆ ವಿಪಿ ಮೆನನ್ ರವರ ಸಹಾಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಲಹೆಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆದು ಪಟೇಲರು ಬಹುತೇಕ ದೇಶೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಥಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಒಕ್ಕೂಟದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಲೀನಗೊಳಿಸಿದರು. ಇದು ಒಂದು ಭಾಗವಾದರೆ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕವಾಗಿ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕವಾಗಿ, ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಇತರೆ ಎಲ್ಲ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅಸಮತೋಲನದಿಂದ ಕೂಡಿದ ವಿವಿಧ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡು ತನ್ನದೇ ಆದ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಆಡಳಿತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳ ಸೇರ್ಪಡೆಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಒಂದು ಸಮಗ್ರ ರಾಜ್ಯವಾಗಿ ರೂಪ ಗೊಂಡಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬಹುದು. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ರಚನೆಯಾಗುವುದಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಮೊದಲೇ ಅಲ್ಲಿ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ತೀಕ್ಷ್ಣವಾದ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮತೋಲನಗಳು ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ ಆ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಬಂದಿರುವುದು ವಿಪರ್ಯಾಯವೇ ಹೌದು. ವಿಶ್ವದ ಎಲ್ಲ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆ ಎಂಬ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯ ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳು ಕಾಣಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಆದರಂತೆ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಈ ಅಂಶವು ಕೆಲವೊಂದು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಪಾರಂಪರಿಕ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಿಂದ ತಿಳಿಯುತ್ತದೆ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿನ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮತೋಲನದ ಮೂಲಗಳನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿದಾಗ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಮತ್ತು ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕಗಳಾಗಿ ವಿಭಜಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಆಧುನಿಕತೆಯ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯನ್ನು ಮುಂದೆ ಇಟ್ಟುಕೊಂಡು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಇಂದು ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕತೆಯ ಕೂಗು ಕೇಳಿ ಬರುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಗಮನಾರ್ಹವಾಗಿದೆ. ಏಕೀಕೃತ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವಾಗಿ ಆರು ದಶಕಗಳೇ ಕಳೆದರೂ ಸಹ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಸ್ವಲ್ಪಬೇಕಾದ ನ್ಯಾಯಯುತ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳು ದೊರೆಯದೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಮಲತಾಯಿ ಧೋರಣೆಯ ನೀತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಒಳಗಾಗಿ ನಿರ್ಲಕ್ಷ್ಯಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಹಾಗೂ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾರಂಭವಾದ ಅನೇಕ ಪ್ರಾಧಿಕಾರಗಳು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನಾಯಕರುಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ಪಾಲಾಗದೆ ಅವುಗಳೆಲ್ಲವೂ ಕೇವಲ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳ ಜನಪ್ರಿಯತೆಗೆ ಅಸ್ತ್ರವಾಗುತ್ತಿವೆಯೇ? ಎಂಬುದು ಒಂದು ಕಡೆಯಾದರೆ ಮತ್ತೊಂದು ಕಡೆ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ಹೆಸರಲ್ಲಿ ಆಯಾ ಪ್ರಾಧಿಕಾರಗಳ ಆಶಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿನ ನಂಬಿಕೆಯೂ ಅದರ ನೀತಿಗಳು ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಇರಲಿಲ್ಲವೇ? ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕವಾದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯನ್ನು ತರಲು ಸರ್ಕಾರ ತಂದಿರುವ ನೀತಿಗಳು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಪೂರಕವಾಗಿಲ್ಲವೇ? ಎಂಬ ಕೆಲವು ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜನರ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯಾದ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕತೆ ಅಥವಾ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯ ಸಾಧ್ಯತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸವಾಲುಗಳ ಕುರಿತಾದ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವೇ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಲೇಖನದ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಮುಖ್ಯ ಪದಗಳು: ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ, ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವ, ಪ್ರಾಂತೀಯತೆ ತಾರತಮ್ಯ, ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕತೆ, ಅನಾಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ.

ಓರೀಕೆ:

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಏಕೀಕರಣದ ಮುಂಚಿತವಾಗಿ ಕನ್ನಡ ಮಾತನಾಡುವಂತಹ ಜನರು ಮತ್ತು ಅವರು ನೆಲೆನಿಂತಿರುವಂತ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳೆಲ್ಲವೂ ಮುಂಬೈ, ಮದ್ರಾಸ್, ಹೈದರಾಬಾದ್ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸೇರಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದವು. ಅಷ್ಟೇ ಅಲ್ಲದೆ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ನೆರೆಯ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಕಾನೂನಿನ ಚೌಕಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿದ್ದವು ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ, ಧಾರವಾಡ, ವಿಜಯಪುರ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತರ ಕನ್ನಡ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಮುಂಬೈ ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯದ ಆಡಳಿತಕ್ಕೆ ಒಳಪಟ್ಟಿದ್ದರೆ ಗುಲ್ಬರ್ಗ, ಬೀದರ್ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಯಚೂರು ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಹೈದರಾಬಾದ್ ನಿಜಾಮನ ಅಧೀನದಲ್ಲಿದ್ದವು. ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕನ್ನಡ ಹಾಗೂ ಬಳ್ಳಾರಿ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಮದ್ರಾಸ್ ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಇದ್ದವು. ಅದರಂತೆಯೇ ಮೈಸೂರು ಸಂಸ್ಥಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂಬತ್ತು ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಿದ್ದವು. ಕೊಡಗು ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿತ್ತು ಎಂಬುದು ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಎಲ್ಲ ಭಾಗಗಳನ್ನು ಒಂದುಗೂಡಿಸಿ ೧೯೫೬ರ ನವಂಬರ್ ೧ರಂದು ಕನ್ನಡ ಮಾತನಾಡುವ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ಒಟ್ಟುಗೂಡಿಸಿ ಏಕೀಕರಣಗೊಳಿಸಿ ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯವನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಇದು ಮೈಸೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಒಂದು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಭಾಷಾ ನೆಲೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಿತು ಆದರೆ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಯಿಂದ ಈ ಏಕೀಕರಣದ ಭೂ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳ ಮಧ್ಯೆ ಅಸಮತೋಲನದ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸಗಳು ಬರತೊಡಗಿದವು. ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ೨೦ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಅವಕಾಶಗಳನ್ನು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಅನುಭವಿಸುತ್ತಿವೆ ಎಂಬ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆ ಈ ತರಹದ ಅಸಮತೋಲನ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸಗಳಿಂದ ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತದೆ.

ಉತ್ತರ-ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಎಂಬುದು ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮತೋಲನದ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಿಂದ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಂಡಂತಹ ಪರಿಭಾವನೆಯಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದರೆ ತಪ್ಪಾಗಲಾರದು. ಇದರಂತೆ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿದೆ, ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಮುಂದುವರೆದ ಪ್ರದೇಶವಾಗಿದೆ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವು ಈ ತೆರನಾದ ವಿಷಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಸಮತೋಲನದ ಮೂಲವನ್ನು ರಾಜ್ಯವು ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಬಂದಾಗಿನಿಂದಲೂ ಗುರುತಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಪುನರ್ ವಿಂಗಡನೆ ಆಯೋಗಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಮುಂಚಿತವಾಗಿ ಜಿವಿಪಿ ಸಮಿತಿ ತನ್ನ ವರದಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಪ್ರದೇಶವು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನದಿಂದ ಪ್ರಗತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಇರುವುದರಿಂದ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪ್ರದೇಶ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಎರಡು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕಗಳನ್ನು ರಚಿಸುವುದು ವಿಹಿತ ಎಂಬ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಕ್ಕೆ ಬಂದಿತ್ತು ಎನ್ನಲಾಗಿದೆ. "ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಮಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಉತ್ತರ ಮತ್ತು ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಗಡಿರೇಖೆಗಳ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖ ಮೊದಲ ಬಾರಿಗೆ ದೊರೆಯುವುದು ಶ್ರೀವಿಜಯನ ಕವಿರಾಜಮಾರ್ಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಕ್ರಿಸ್ತಶಕ ೯ನೇ ಶತಮಾನದ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಕೂಟ ಅಮೋಘವರ್ಷ ನೃಪತುಂಗನ ಇದರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾವೇರಿಯಿಂದಮಾ ಗೋದಾವರಿ ವರಮಿಧನ ನಾಡದ ಕನ್ನಡದೊಳೆ"³, ಎಂದು ಕನ್ನಡ ನಾಡಿನ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತರ ಗಡಿಗಳನ್ನು ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸಿದೆ.

ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕತೆ ಬೇಡಿಕೆ ಸಾಧ್ಯವೇ?

ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕವಾಗಿ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುವ ಹದಿಮೂರು ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಇತಿಹಾಸದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿವೆ, ಈ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಹಳೆಯ ಮುಂಬೈ ಮತ್ತು ಹೈದರಾಬಾದ್ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳ ಭಾಗಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿವೆ. ಮತ್ತು ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕಕ್ಕೆ ಹೋಲಿಸಿದರೆ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕತೆ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯಿಂದಾಗಿ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದಿದೆ ಎಂದು ತಿಳಿದು ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಣ್ಣ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯು ಸಾಧಾರಣವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ, ಆದರೆ ಕೆಲವು ದೊಡ್ಡ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳು ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕವಾಗಿ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಲು ತೊಡಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ

³ ಗೋಪಾಲ್ ರಾವ್ ಎಚ್‌ಎಸ್ ೨೦೧೨ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಏಕೀಕರಣ ಇತಿಹಾಸ ನವ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪಬ್ಲಿಕೇಶನ್.

ಇದಲ್ಲದೆ ರಾಜ್ಯದೊಳಗಿನ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ವೈವಿಧ್ಯಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಗಳು, ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕತಾವಾದಿ ಕಲ್ಪನೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ವೇಗವನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತವೆ. ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕತಾವಾದಿ ಚಳುವಳಿಯ ನಾಯಕರು ತಮ್ಮ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಯಾವುದೇ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಬಂದರೂ ಸಹ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿದಾಯಕ ನೀತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಗೊಳಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಫಲವಾಗಿವೆ ಎನ್ನುವುದು ಅವರ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಕಂಡಂತಹ ಬಹುತೇಕ ಮುಖ್ಯಮಂತ್ರಿಗಳು ರಾಜ್ಯದ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳ ನಾಯಕರುಗಳಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಅದರ ಪರಿಣಾಮವಾಗಿ ಅವರ ನೀತಿಗಳು ಉತ್ತರಕ್ಕಿಂತ ದಕ್ಷಿಣಕ್ಕೆ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನವನ್ನು ಪಡೆದಿದೆ ಎಂಬುವುದು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಜನರ ಮತ್ತೊಂದು ವಾದವಾಗಿದೆ. ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯ ಕೂಗು ದಶಕಗಳಷ್ಟೇ ಹಳೆಯದು ಆದರೆ ಅದರ ಕಾರಣಗಳು ಕಾಲ ನಂತರದಲ್ಲಿ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಯಾಗುತ್ತಾ ಬರುತ್ತಿವೆ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ದಕ್ಷಿಣದಿಂದ ಬಂದಿರುವ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ನಾಯಕರು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವನ್ನು ಕಡೆಗಣಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂಬ ಭಾವನೆ ಈ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯ ಮುಖ್ಯ ತಿರುಳಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದಲ್ಲದೆ ಏಕೀಕರಣದ ಮೊದಲು ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಅಧಿಕಾರವೂ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಿಗೆ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತವಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ನಂತರ ಅದು ಬದಲಾಯಿತು ಮತ್ತು ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಭಾಗಕ್ಕೆ ಸ್ಥಳಾಂತರಗೊಂಡಿತ್ತು ಎಂಬ ವಿಚಾರಗಳು ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕತೆಯ ಸುತ್ತ ಕೇಳಿ ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಾಗಾದರೆ ಏಕೀಕರಣದ ಮೊದಲು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಅಖಂಡತೆಗೆ ಶ್ರಮಿಸಿದ ಕೀರ್ತಿಯು ಸಹ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ನಾಯಕರಾಗಿದ್ದ ಸಲ್ಲುತ್ತದೆ. ಏಕೀಕರಣಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಹೋರಾಡಿ ದಂತಹ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಜನರು ಯಾಕೆ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕತೆಯ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ತರುತ್ತಾರೆ ಎಂಬ ವಿಚಾರವನ್ನು ನಾವಿಲ್ಲಿ ಗಂಭೀರವಾಗಿ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ, ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ೧೩ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಇತ್ತೀಚೆಗೆ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಹೊಸ ಕೂಗು ಎಬ್ಬಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಹೊಸದೇನಲ್ಲ. ಯಾಕೆಂದರೆ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಪೂರ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವನ್ನು ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕವಾಗಿ ನಿರ್ಲಕ್ಷ್ಯ ಒಳಪಟ್ಟಿದೆ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಏಕೀಕರಣದ ನಂತರ ನಿರಾಶಕ್ತಿ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದಿರುವಿಕೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವೆಂದು ಹೇಳಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

“ಮೈಸೂರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಎರಡು ಬಣಗಳು ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಬಂದವು ಆದರೆ ಯಾವ ಬಣವು ಬಹಿರಂಗವಾಗಿ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದವರ ಕಲ್ಪನೆಯ ಏಕೀಕರಣವನ್ನು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ಬೆಂಬಲಿಸಲಿಲ್ಲ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ವ್ಯಾಪಕ ಜನಾಂದೋಲನ ಸಂಘಟಿಸಲು ವಿದ್ಯುಕ್ತವಾದರೆ ಮೈಸೂರಿಗರು ತೆರೆಮರೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಆ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಚರ್ಚಿಸಿ ತೊಡಗಿದರು”⁴ ಎಂಬುದು ಕೆಲವು ವಿದ್ವಾಂಸರ ವಿಚಾರಗಳಿಂದ ತಿಳಿದು ಬರುತ್ತದೆ ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ “ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಮೈಸೂರಿಗೆ ಸೇರಿದರೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಏರುಪೇರಾಗಿ ಲಿಂಗಾಯತರು ಪ್ರಬಲರಾಗುತ್ತಾರೆ ಎಂಬ ಸಂಶಯವು ಹಲವರಲ್ಲಿತ್ತು ಆಗ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಾಬಲ್ಯ ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದ ಮೈಸೂರಿನ ಒಕ್ಕಲಿಗ ಸಮುದಾಯವು ತನ್ನ ಪ್ರಾಬಲ್ಯ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದೆಂಬ ಆತಂಕವು ಇತ್ತು”⁵ ಈ ರೀತಿಯ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಅಂದಿನ ರಾಜ್ಯ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಒಳಗಡೆ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕತೆಯ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿ ಜಾತಿ ಅಸ್ಥಿತಿಯು ಒಂದು ನೆಪವಾಗಿ ಅದರ ಮೂಲಕ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಹಿಂದುಳಿಯಲು ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಈ ಒಂದು ನಿಲುವಿನಿಂದ ತಿಳಿಯುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದರಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತೊಂದು ಅಂಶವನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿದರೆ “ಆಧುನಿಕೋತ್ತರ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿ ಈ ಅಸ್ಥಿತೆ ಒಂದು ಸಮಗ್ರ ವಿಶಾಲವೆಂದು ಹೊರನೋಟಕ್ಕೆ ಕಂಡುಬಂದರು, ಅದರ ಆಳಕ್ಕೆ ಇಳಿದಾಗ ಅದರ ವಿಧಳತೆಯ ದನಿಗಳನ್ನು ನೋಡಬಹುದು. ಉದಾರಣೆಗೆ ಗೋಕಾಕ್ ಚಳುವಳಿ ಸಮಗ್ರತೆಯ ಸಂಕೇತವಾದರೆ ರೈತ ಚಳುವಳಿ, ದಲಿತ ಚಳುವಳಿ, ಪರಿಸರ ಚಳುವಳಿ, ಮಹಿಳಾ ಚಳುವಳಿಗಳು

⁴ ಚಂದ್ರಶೇಖರ್ ಎಸ್ ೨೦೦೫ ಏಕೀಕರಣ ಒಂದು ಕಥನ ಸತ್ಯ ಶ್ರೀ ಪ್ರಿಂಟರ್ಸ್ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು.

⁵ ಅದೇ ಪುಸ್ತಕ ಪು.ಸಂ 41

ವಿಧಳತೆಯ ಸಂಕೇತಗಳಾಗುತ್ತವೆ.⁶ ಅಂದರೆ ಇವು ಆಧುನಿಕೋತ್ತರ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿ ತಮ್ಮನ್ನು ತಾವು ಹಿಂದುಳಿದಿರುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಲ್ಲಿ ಅವುಗಳ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಕಾಣಲು ಸಿಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಚಿತ್ರವೆಂದರೆ ಈ ತರಹದ ಅಸ್ಥಿತ್ವಗಳು ಒಂದಕ್ಕೊಂದು ಅನುಸಂಧಾನ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿರುತ್ತವೆ ಅಥವಾ ಮುಖಾಮುಖಿಯಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ, ಆದರೂ ಸಹ ಇವುಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ಒಂದರಡು ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ದೃಶ್ಯಗಳಿವೆ ಅಂತೆಯೇ ಕೊಡಗು ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕತೆ ಚಳುವಳಿ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕತೆಯ ಹೋರಾಟ ಇವುಗಳು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಶ್ನಿಸುವಂತಹ ಅಸ್ಥಿತ್ವಗಳಾಗಿವೆ. ಈ ರೀತಿಯ ಹೋರಾಟಗಳ ಹಿಂದೆ ಗತಕಾಲದ ವೈಭವದ ವರ್ಣನೆಗಳಿವೆ, ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕವಾದ ತಾರತಮ್ಯದ ಕಥನಗಳಿವೆ, ಅಸ್ಥಿತ್ವ ಸಂಘರ್ಷಗಳು, ತಾಖಲಾಟಗಳು, ಪ್ರತಿರೋಧಗಳು ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಮಹತ್ವವಾದ ಪರಿಣಾಮವನ್ನು ಬೀರುತ್ತದೆ.

೨೦೦೦ ವರ್ಷದ ಆರಂಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಕಾರ್ಯಕರ್ತರಾದ ವೈಜಂತ ಪಾಟೀಲ ಅವರು ಹೈದರಾಬಾದ್ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವನ್ನು ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ರಾಜ್ಯವನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡಬೇಕೆಂದು ಒತ್ತಾಯಿಸಿದರು. ಆ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯು ಇವತ್ತಿನ ರೀತಿಯ ಕಾಳಜಿಯಿಂದ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಂಡಿತ್ತು. ಆದರೆ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಬಗೆಗಿನ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನಾಯಕರ ನಿರಾಸಕ್ತಿ ಹೊಂದಿರುವುದೇ ಕಾರಣ ಎಂದು ಆರೋಪಿಸಿದ್ದರು ಹಾಗಾದರೆ ಯಾವ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದವರ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಗಮನಹರಿಸಲಿಲ್ಲವೇ ಎಂದು ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಾಗ ೨೦೦೦ ರಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಶ್ರೀ ಎಸ್ ಎಂ ಕೃಷ್ಣರವರ ನೇತೃತ್ವದ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮತೋಲನ ನಿವಾರಣೆಗಾಗಿ ಉನ್ನತಾಧಿಕಾರ ಸಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು "ಪ್ರೊಫೆಸರ್ ಡಿ ಎಂ ನಂಜುಂಡಪ್ಪನವರ ಅಧ್ಯಕ್ಷತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ರೂಪಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಆ ಒಂದು ಸಮಿತಿಯು ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮತೋಲನಗಳ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿ ೨೦೦೩ ರಲ್ಲಿ ತನ್ನ ಸಮಗ್ರ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ವರದಿಯನ್ನು ಸರ್ಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಒಪ್ಪಿಸಲಾಯಿತು."⁷ ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ೩೯ ತಾಲೂಕುಗಳು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದಿವೆ ಎಂದು ಪಟ್ಟಿ ಮಾಡಿತ್ತು ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ೨೬ ತಾಲೂಕುಗಳು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದವಗಳಾಗಿವೆ ಈ ತಾಲೂಕುಗಳ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿರುವ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳ ಪ್ರಮಾಣವನ್ನು ಸಮಿತಿಯು ಸೂಚಿಸಿತು ಲೆ ವರ್ಷಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ೧೬ ಸಾವಿರ ಕೋಟಿ ರೂಪಾಯಿಯ ವಿಶೇಷ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸುಗಳನ್ನು ಸೂಚಿಸಿತು ಆದರೆ ನಂತರ ಬಂದು ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಈ ವಿಷಯದ ಬಗೆಗೆ ಮೌನವಾಗಿ ಬಿಟ್ಟಿರುವುದು ವಿಪರ್ಯಾಯವೇ ಸರಿ. ಮುಂದೆ ಶ್ರೀ ಹೆಚ್ ಡಿ ಕುಮಾರಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಅವರ ಬಚೆಟ್ ನಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹದಾಯಿ ಜಲ ವಿವಾದಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಧೋರಣೆಗಳು ಸಮರ್ಪಕವಾಗಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ಅಲ್ಲಿನ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಹೋರಾಟ ಸಮಿತಿ ಹಲವು ಬಾರಿ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಬಂದ್ ಗೆ ಕರೆ ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದ್ದು ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಾವು ಕಾಣಬಹುದು.

ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಹೋರಾಟ ಸಮಿತಿಯ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪ್ರದೇಶವು ನೈಸರ್ಗಿಕ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳಿಂದ ಸಮೃದ್ಧವಾಗಿದ್ದರೂ ನಿರುದ್ಯೋಗದಂತಹ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳು ಬಗೆಹರಿಯುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ. ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕತೆಯ ಅಸಮತೋಲನ ನಿವಾರಣೆಗಾಗಿ ಪ್ರೊಫೆಸರ್ ನಂಜುಂಡಪ್ಪ ಸಮಿತಿಯ ವರದಿಯ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸುಗಳನ್ನು ಯಥಾವತ್ತಾಗಿ ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತರುವಲ್ಲಿ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ವಿಫಲವಾಗಿದ್ದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಈ

⁶ ಅಸಾದಿ ಮುಜಾಫರ್ ೨೦೧೭ ಅಸ್ಥಿತ್ವ ರಾಜಕಾರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಮೂಲಭೂತವಾದ ಕೆಲವು ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳು ಲಡಾಯಿ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ ಗದಗ.

⁷ ಅಥಣಿ ಬಸಪ್ಪತಡಸದ ಕಮಲಾಕ್ಷಿರಾಮಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಹರೀಶ್. ೨೦೨೩. ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕಾರಣ, ಜಡಭಾರತ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ, ಧಾರವಾಡ.

ಪ್ರದೇಶ ಬಡತನದಿಂದ ಬಳಲುತ್ತಿದೆ ನಮ್ಮ ಭಾಗದ ರೈತರು ಹಲವು ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುವಂತೆ ಆಗಿದೆ ಈ ಹಿಂದಿನ ಎಲ್ಲ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಬಜೆಟ್ ನಲ್ಲಿ ಅತ್ಯಲ್ಪ ಹಣವನ್ನು ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಿವೆ. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಎನ್ನುವುದು ಕೇವಲ ಮರಿಚಿಕೆಯಾಗಿ, ಈ ತರಹದ ಧೋರಣೆಗಳು ಮುಂದುವರಿಯುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಅದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವನ್ನು ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ರಾಜ್ಯವನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡಬೇಕೆಂದು ಹೋರಾಟ ಸಮಿತಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಜನರ ಧ್ವನಿಯಾಗಿದೆ.

ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕತೆ ಬೇಡಿಕೆ ಸಾಧುವೆ?

ಇಂದಿನ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ನಕ್ಷೆಯನ್ನು ನೋಡಿದಾಗ ನಮಗೆ ಸಾವಿರಾರು ವರ್ಷಗಳ ಹೋರಾಟದ ಚಾರಿತ್ರಿಕ ಘಟನೆಗಳು ನೆನಪಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ರೂಪಕ್ಕೆ ಬರಬೇಕು ಎಷ್ಟೋ ರಾಜವಂಶಗಳು, ಸಾಹಿತಿಗಳು ,ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ,ಕವಿಗಳು ,ಬುದ್ಧಿ ಜೀವಿಗಳು ಮಾಡಿದಂತಹ ಹೋರಾಟವು ನಮಗೆ ಸರಿಯಾಗಿ ತಿಳಿಯದು. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಏಕೀಕರಣದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯ ಚಿಂತನೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿದವರಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಧಾರವಾಡದ ಡೆಪ್ಯೂಟಿ ಚಿನ್ನಬಸವಪ್ಪನವರು ಎಂಬುದು ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಏಕೀಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಮೊದಲು ಮೈಸೂರು ಸಂಸ್ಥಾನದ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಾದ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ, ಧಾರವಾಡ, ಬಿಜಾಪುರ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತರ ಕನ್ನಡ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಮಹಾರಾಜರಿಂದ ನಿರ್ಲಕ್ಷ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಒಳಪಟ್ಟವು. ಅತ್ತ ಹೈದರಾಬಾದಿನ ನಿಜಾಮನ ಆಳ್ವಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿದ್ದ ಗುಲ್ಬರ್ಗ, ರಾಯಚೂರು ಮತ್ತು ಬೀದರ್ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಕೂಡ ಬರಗಾಲ ಡಕಾಯಿತರ ಹಾವಳಿಗಳಿಂದ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆ ಹೊಂದುವಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಫಲವಾಗಿದ್ದವು ಮದ್ರಾಸ್ ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿದ ಬಳ್ಳಾರಿ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರವನ್ನು ಉಪಮಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸಿದ್ದರೂ ಸಹ ಮೈಸೂರು ಪ್ರಾಂತ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಹೋಲಿಸಿದರೆ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಎಂಬುವುದು ಕನಸಿನ ಮಾತಾಗಿಯೇ ಕಾಣುತ್ತಿತ್ತು. ಈ ಎಲ್ಲ ಕಾರಣಗಳಿಂದ ಬೇಸತ್ತು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜನತೆ ಭಾಷಾವಾರು ಏಕೀಕೃತ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಿಂದಲೇ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಸಾಧ್ಯ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ತಿಳಿದು ಏಕೀಕರಣದ ಕಹಳೆಯನ್ನು ಮೊಳಗಿಸಿದರು.

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಏಕೀಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಪೂರಕವಾಗಿ ಧಾರವಾಡದಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಥಾಪನೆಯಾದಂತೆ ವಿದ್ಯಾವರ್ಧಕ ಸಂಘ, ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಏಕೀಕರಣ ಸಮಿತಿ, ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಸಭೆಗಳು ಮಹತ್ವದ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಿದವು ಇವರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ವಿಶಾಲ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ, ನವಯುಗ, ಪ್ರಪಂಚ, ವಾಗ್ಗೂಷಣ ಪತ್ರಿಕೆಗಳು ಏಕೀಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಮಹತ್ವಪೂರ್ಣವಾದ ಕೊಡುಗೆ ನೀಡಿವೆ ಈ ರೀತಿ ಅಖಂಡ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ವಾಗಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಪಾತ್ರ ಹೀರಿದಾಗಿದೆ. ಅಖಂಡ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಕನಸನ್ನು ಕಂಡಂತಹ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜನರು ಯಾಕೆ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಇಡುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ನಿಜವೇ ಒಂದು ವೇಳೆ ನಿಜವಾಗಿದ್ದರೆ ಯಾವ ಉದ್ದೇಶಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಅವರು ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಮುಂದಿಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಅಂತ ಗಮನಿಸಿದಾಗ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಬೇಡಿಕೆ ಅಲ್ಲ ಅದು ಆ ಭಾಗದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮಾತ್ರ ಕೇಳುತ್ತಿದೆ ನಮಗೆ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಬೇಡ ಈ ಪ್ರದೇಶ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಆಗಬೇಕು ಎಂದು ಅಲ್ಲಿನ ಜನರ ಬಯಕೆಯಾಗಿದೆ ಎನ್ನುವುದು ಕೆಲವು ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳಿಂದ ತಿಳಿದು ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಬೆಳಗಾವಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸುವರ್ಣ ಸೌಧ ಉದ್ಘಾಟನೆಯಾದಾಗ ಅದನ್ನು ಉದ್ಘಾಟಿಸಿದ ಅಂದಿನ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಪತಿಗಳು ಸುವರ್ಣ ಸೌಧವು ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವಲ್ಲಿ ಅತಿ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಕೇಂದ್ರವಾಗಬೇಕು ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಿದ್ದರು. ಅದರಂತೆಯೇ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರಿನಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಕೆಲವು ಕಚೇರಿಗಳನ್ನು ನೇರವಾಗಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಕೆಲವು ಕಚೇರಿಗಳನ್ನು ವಿಭಜಿಸಿ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕಕ್ಕೆ ಸ್ಥಳಾಂತರಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಅವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ "ಕೃಷ್ಣ ಭಾಗ್ಯ ಜಲ ನಿಗಮ ನಿಯಮಿತ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಕಚೇರಿಯನ್ನು ಆಲಮಟ್ಟಿಗೆ, ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಜವಳಿ ಮೂಲ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ನಿಗಮ ನಿಯಮಿತ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ಕಚೇರಿಯನ್ನು ಬೆಳಗಾವಿಗೆ, ಸಕ್ಕರೆ ನಿರ್ದೇಶಕರು ಮತ್ತು ಕಬ್ಬು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಆಯುಕ್ತ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಕಚೇರಿಯನ್ನು ಬೆಂಗಳೂರಿನಿಂದ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿಗೆ ಈ ರೀತಿಯಾಗಿ ಹಲವು ಪ್ರಾಧಿಕಾರಗಳು ಉತ್ತರ

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಅನುಕೂಲದ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಯಿಂದಾಗಿ ಸ್ಥಳಾಂತರಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.⁸ ಹಾಗೂ ನಿಧಾನಗತಿಯ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಯ ನಂತರ ಹವಾಮಾನ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಗಳು ಅತಿರೇಕಕ್ಕೆ ಏರಿ ಹಲವು ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸಗಳು ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕವಾಗಿ ಉಲ್ಬನಗೊಂಡವು ಉತ್ತರದಲ್ಲಿ ನೇಮಕಗೊಂಡ ಅನೇಕ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ನೌಕರರು ಮೊದಲ ಅವಕಾಶದಲ್ಲಿ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಿಗೆ ವರ್ಗಾಯಿಸಲು ಬಯಸುವುದರಲ್ಲಿ ಆಶ್ಚರ್ಯವಿಲ್ಲ ಮತ್ತು ನಮ್ಮದೇ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ನಾಯಕರ ನಿರಾಶಕ್ತಿಯಿಂದಾಗಿ ಈ ರೀತಿಯ ಎದ್ದು ಕಾಣುವ ಭಿನ್ನಾಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಗಳು ನಮ್ಮನ್ನು ಕಡೆಗಣಿಸಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ಭಾವಿಸುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದೆ.

ಈ ತರಹದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಂದ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಎತ್ತುವುದು ಸಮಂಜಸವಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಆಂತರಿಕವಾಗಿ ಇರುವ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಾಗ ಅಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಹಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಕಂಡುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ಬೇಡಿಕೆ ಮುಂದೆ ಇಟ್ಟುಕೊಂಡು ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ಮತ್ತಷ್ಟು ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಬಹುತೇಕ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳು ಮುಂದಾಗುತ್ತೇವೆ ಎನ್ನುವುದು ಈ ಮೇಲಿನ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳಿಂದ ತಿಳಿಯುತ್ತದೆ. ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ತರದ ಶಾಸಕರು ದಕ್ಷಿಣದ ಶಾಸಕರಂತೆ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲರಾಗಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ಕೆಲವರ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಪಟ್ಟರೆ ಮತ್ತೆ ಕೆಲವರು ಉತ್ತರ ಭಾಗದ ಶಾಸಕರು ಇಂದಿಗೂ ಉಳಿಗಮಾನ್ಯ ಮನೋಭಾವದವರು ಸ್ವಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಭಾವನೆ ಇಲ್ಲದವರು ಎನ್ನುವಂತಹ ಹಲವರ ವಾದಗಳಿವೆ. ಅದರೊಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಇತ್ತೀಚಿಗೆ ಅತಿಯಾದ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರ ಸೇರಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದು ಇವು ಈ ಭಾಗದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಮಾರಕವಾಗಿದೆ ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಅಖಂಡ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕವನ್ನು ಕಟ್ಟಲು ಶ್ರಮಿಸಿದ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜನತೆ ತಾವುಗಳು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಸಾಧಿಸಲು ಬೇಕಾದ ನೀತಿ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಅವುಗಳ ಕಾರ್ಯ ಸಾಧನೆಗೆ ಮುಂದಾಗಬೇಕು. ಅವಾಗ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕವಾಗಿ ಅಸಮತೋಲನದ ಅಂಶವನ್ನು ಅಳಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ಎಚ್ಚರಿಸುವ ಹಾಗೂ ಒಳ್ಳೆಯ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನಾಯಕರನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆಗೊಳಿಸಿ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಏಳಿಗೆಗೆ ಶ್ರಮಿಸುವ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಮುಂದಾದಾಗ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯ ಕೂಗು ಕೇಳಿ ಬರುವುದು ಕಡಿಮೆಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಾಗೆ ನೋಡಿದರೆ "ನಂಜುಂಡಪ್ಪ ಸಮಿತಿಯ ಸೂಚಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಎಲ್ಲ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದರಿಂದ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜೀವನ ಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ಉದಾಹರಣೆ ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಹೈದರಾಬಾದ್ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ವಿಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಜನರು ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಸಮರ್ಥವಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಖುಷಿಯ ವಿಚಾರವಾದರೂ ಈ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಸಮಾನತೆ ಎನ್ನುವುದು ಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ ನಿವಾರಣೆಯಾಗಿಲ್ಲ."⁹ ಹಾಗಂತ ಹೇಳಿ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯು ಸಾಧ್ಯವೆ? ಬಂದಾಗ ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ಪೂರಕವಾಗಿ ವಿಚಾರ ಮಾಡಿದರೆ ನಂಜುಂಡಪ್ಪ ಸಮಿತಿಯ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸುಗಳನ್ನು ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು ರೂಪದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾಮಾಣಿಕವಾಗಿ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಜಾರಿಗೆ

⁸ ಅಥಣಿ ಬಸಪ್ಪ, ತಡಸದ ಕಮಲಾಕ್ಷಿ, ರಾಮಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಹರೀಶ್. ೨೦೨೩. ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕಾರಣ, ಜಡಭಾರತ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ, ಧಾರವಾಡ.

⁹ ಅಥಣಿ ಬಸಪ್ಪ, ತಡಸದ ಕಮಲಾಕ್ಷಿ, ರಾಮಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಹರೀಶ್. ೨೦೨೩. ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕಾರಣ, ಜಡಭಾರತ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ, ಧಾರವಾಡ. ಪು, ಸಂ. ೨೨೭.

ತರುವುದು ಹಾಗೂ ತರುವ ಹಾಗೆ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜನದ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯಾಗಬೇಕು, ಹೊರತು ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕದ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯ ಕೂಗು ಸಾಧ್ಯ ಅಲ್ಲ ಅನ್ನುವಂತ ಅಂಶಗಳು ಇದರಿಂದ ತಿಳಿದು ಬರುತ್ತದೆ.

ಸಾಧ್ಯತೆಗಳು :

- ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ರೂಪಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಪ್ರೊಫೆಸರ್ ನಂಬುಂಡಪ್ಪನವರ ಸಮಿತಿಯ ವರದಿಯ ಶಿಫಾರಸುಗಳನ್ನು ಯಥಾವತ್ತಾಗಿ ಕಾರ್ಯರೂಪಕ್ಕೆ ತರುವಲ್ಲಿ ಆಯಾ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಕಾರ್ಯ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಲು ಮುಂದಾಗಬೇಕು.
- ತಳಮಟ್ಟದಿಂದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅರಿತು ಲಭ್ಯವಿರುವ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳನ್ನು ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಯಾವ ರೀತಿ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಸಾಧಿಸಬೇಕೆನ್ನುವಂತಹ ಯೋಜನೆ ರೂಪಿಸಿ ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸುವುದರಿಂದ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಸಮತೋಲನ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.
- ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಜನರಿಗೆ ಸಮರ್ಪಕವಾಗಿ ತಿಳಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಹಿಂದೆ ಬಿದ್ದಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಯೋಜನೆಯನ್ನು ಫಲಾನುಭವಿಗಳಿಗೆ ನೀಡಲು ಸಹಾಯಕಾರಿಯಾದ ಕೌಶಲ್ಯ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಪಡಿಸುವುದು ಇಂದಿನ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆ.
- ಜನಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳಿಗೆ ತಮ್ಮ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿನ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅರಿತು ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಗತಿಯನ್ನು ಸುಧಾರಿಸಬಹುದು ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಅರಿಯಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ.
- ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳನ್ನು ಸರಿಯಾಗಿ ಬಳಕೆಯಾಗುವಂತೆ ಕೈಗಾರಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಬೇಕು.
- ಕೃಷಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸುಧಾರಣೆ ತರಲು ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಕಾನೂನು, ನೀರಾವರಿ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಬೇಕು. ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಆ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಅನೇಕ ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಸ್ಥಳಗಳಿಗೆ ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರವಾಸಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರಗಳನ್ನಾಗಿ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಪಡಿಸಿ ಕ್ರಮ ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.

ಸಮಾರೂಪ

ಈ ಮೇಲಿನ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳಿಂದ ತಿಳಿದುಬರುವುದೇನೆಂದರೆ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾನವ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯು ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಯಿಂದ ಕೂಡಿದೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳು ಮಾನವ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಉನ್ನತ ಮಟ್ಟದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿವೆ ಅಂದರೆ ಅವರ ಜೀವನಮಟ್ಟ ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಕೈಗಾರಿಕೆ ಉದ್ಯಮ ಹಾಗೂ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ವಲಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೋಲಿಸಿದಾಗ ಉತ್ತಮ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಹೊಂದಿರುವುದು ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತದೆ ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಕಳೆದ ಹಲವಾರು ವರ್ಷಗಳ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂವಿಧಾನಾತ್ಮಕ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ಬಂಡವಾಳ ತೊಡಗಿಸಿದ್ದರು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ನೀತಿಗಳು ಅಥವಾ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳು ಕೆಳಹಂತದ ಜನರಿಗೆ ತಲುಪುವುದರ ಮೂಲಕ ಅವರ ಜೀವನದ ಗುಣಮಟ್ಟ ನಿರೀಕ್ಷಿತ ಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಆಗದೆ ಇರುವುದು ವಿಪರ್ಯಾಸವೇ ಸರಿ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನದ ಕೊರತೆಯೇ ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ. ಅದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಉತ್ತಮ ಗುಣಮಟ್ಟದ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ, ಆರೋಗ್ಯ, ಆಧುನಿಕ ಕೌಶಲ್ಯಗಳ ಪೂರೈಕೆ, ಉದ್ಯೋಗಾವಕಾಶಗಳ ಸೃಷ್ಟಿ, ನೀರಾವರಿ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳ ಪೂರೈಕೆ, ಸಮಗ್ರ ಕೃಷಿ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆ, ಆಹಾರ ಭದ್ರತೆಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುವುದು, ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಸೌಕರ್ಯಗಳ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಕಡೆಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಆದ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದಾಗ ಈ ತೆರನಾದ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಅಸಮತೋಲನದ ಕೂಗಿನ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯ ಕೂಗುಗಳು ಕೇಳಿ ಬರಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂಬುದು ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆ ಲೇಖನದ ಸಾರವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಆಧಾರ ಗ್ರಂಥಗಳು

ಗೋಪಾಲ್ ರಾವ್ ಎಚ್‌ಎಸ್. ೨೦೧೨. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಏಕೀಕರಣ ಇತಿಹಾಸ ನವ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪಬ್ಲಿಕೇಶನ್ಸ್.

ಅಥಣಿ ಬಸವಪ್ಪತಡಸದ ಕಮಲಾಕ್ಷಿ.ರಾಮಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಹರೀಶ್. ೨೦೨೩. ಉತ್ತರ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕಾರಣ, ಜಡಭಾರತ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ, ಧಾರವಾಡ.

ಚಂದ್ರಶೇಖರ್ ಎಸ್ ೨೦೦೫ ಏಕೀಕರಣ ಒಂದು ಕಥನ ಸತ್ಯ ಶ್ರೀ ಪ್ರಿಂಟರ್ಸ್ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು.

ಗವಿಮಠ ಬಿಎಸ್ ೨೦೧೧ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ ಕನ್ನಡ ಕನ್ನಡಿಗ ಪ್ರಗತಿ ಪ್ರಿಂಟ್ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು.

ನಾಗಭೂಷಣ್ ಡಿಎಸ್ ೨೦೦೯ ಕನ್ನಡ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಸಂಕಥನಗಳು ವಿಸ್ಮಯ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ ಮೈಸೂರು.

ಜಾಮದಾರ್ ಶಿವಾನಂದ ೨೦೧೬ ತಾರತಮ್ಯ ಮನೋಹರ್ ಗ್ರಂಥಮಾಲಾ ಧಾರವಾಡ.

ಚಂದ್ರ ಪೂಜಾರಿ ಎಂ ೨೦೧೮ ಪ್ರಸಾರಂಗ ಕನ್ನಡ ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ ಹಂಪಿ.

ಅಸಾದಿ ಮುಜಾಫರ್ ೨೦೧೭ ಅಸ್ಮಿತೆ ರಾಜಕಾರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಮೂಲಭೂತವಾದ ಕೆಲವು ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳು ಲಡಾಯಿ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ ಗದಗ.

ಕೇಶವ ಶರ್ಮಾ ಕೆ ೨೦೧೧ ವಸಾಹತುಶಾಹಿ ಅನುಭವ ಪೂರ್ಣಪ್ರಕಾಶನ ಶಿವಮೊಗ್ಗ.

ಅ ಕ್ರಿಟಿಕಲ್ ಅನಾಲಿಸಿಸ್ ಆಫ್ ಡಾ. ಡಿಎಂ ನಂಜುಂಡಪ್ಪ ಕಮಿಟಿ ರಿಪೋರ್ಟ್ ಡಾ. ವಿಜಯಕುಮಾರ್ ಸಾಲಿಮನಿ.

<https://swarajyamag.com/ideas/north-karnataka-statehood-weneed-a-new-states-reorganisation-commission>

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ಭಾರತದ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಪಾತ್ರ

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Abstract

ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಆಡಳಿತದ ಮೂಲಾಧಾರವಾಗಿ ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯುಳ್ಳ ಮತ್ತು ತರ್ಕಬದ್ಧ ಚರ್ಚೆಯ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯು ಒತ್ತಿಹೇಳುತ್ತದೆ. ಭಾರತೀಯ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ, ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಸಂವಾದವನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ, ನೀತಿ-ನಿರೂಪಣೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ನಾಗರಿಕರನ್ನು ತೊಡಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಪೋಷಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಚರ್ಚಾ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ನಿರ್ಣಾಯಕ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಲೇಖನವು ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ, ಅಂತರ್ಗತ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಸಕ್ರಿಯಗೊಳಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಖಾತ್ರಿಪಡಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ-ಪತ್ರಿಕೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ದೂರದರ್ಶನದಂತಹ ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕ ವೇದಿಕೆಗಳಿಂದ ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದವರೆಗೆ-ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಬಹುಮುಖಿ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೋಧಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಪತ್ರಿಕೆಯು ತಪ್ಪು, ಮಾಹಿತಿ, ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಪಕ್ಷಪಾತ ಮತ್ತು ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ವಿಭಜನೆಯಿಂದ ಉಂಟಾಗುವ ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಕೂಡ ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಲೇಖನವು ಭಾರತೀಯ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ಬಲಪಡಿಸಲು ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವನ್ನು ಎತ್ತಿ ತೋರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅವುಗಳ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಅಡ್ಡಿಯಾಗುವ ಅಡೆತಡೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ವಿಕಸನವು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪುನಃ ಮಾಡುವ ವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ಮಾತ್ರವಲ್ಲದೆ ನಾಗರಿಕರು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ಹೇಗೆ ತೊಡಗಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಸಹ ಬದಲಾಯಿಸಿದೆ, ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಭಾಷಣ, ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಕಾಲೀನ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ನಾಗರಿಕ ತೊಡಗಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆಗೆ ನಿರ್ಣಾಯಕ ವೇದಿಕೆಯಾಗಿ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಪ್ರಬಂಧವು ಈ ಕ್ರಿಯಾತ್ಮಕ ಭೂದೃಶ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಚಾರಶೀಲ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೋಧಿಸುತ್ತದೆ, ನಾಗರಿಕರಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯುಳ್ಳ ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸುಗಮಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ನೀತಿಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ಬಹು ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನಗಳನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುವ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವನ್ನು ಎತ್ತಿ ತೋರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪದಗಳು: ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ (ಡೆಲಿಬರೇಟಿವ್ ಡೆಮಾಕ್ರಸಿ), ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ, ಸುದ್ದಿ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ, ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ವೇದಿಕೆ, ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯ

ಭಾರತದ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಪಾತ್ರ

ಪೀಠಿಕೆ:

ಆಧುನಿಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವಗಳಲ್ಲಿ, ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧಿಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಪರ್ಯಾಯವಾಗಿ ಅಥವಾ ಪೂರಕವಾಗಿ ಚಿಂತನಶೀಲ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಆಸಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ವಿವೇಚನಾಶೀಲ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವು ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯುಳ್ಳ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ಮುಕ್ತವಾಗಿ ಹಂಚಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದರ ಮೇಲೆ ಅವಲಂಬಿತವಾಗಿದೆ. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಇದು ಸಾಮೂಹಿಕ ನಿರ್ಧಾರ ಮತ್ತು ನೀತಿ-ನಿರೂಪಣೆಯನ್ನು ಸುಲಭಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದು ಚಿಂತನಶೀಲ ಸಂಭಾಷಣೆ, ಮುಕ್ತ

ಸಂವಹನ ಮತ್ತು ನಿರ್ಧಾರ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸಕ್ರಿಯ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮೂಹ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಪಾತ್ರವು ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ತಜ್ಞರು, ನಿರ್ಧಾರ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವವರು ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯಕರ್ತರಿಗೆ ಆಸಕ್ತಿಯ ನಿರ್ಣಾಯಕ ವಿಷಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ರೇಡಿಯೋ, ದೂರದರ್ಶನ, ವೃತ್ತಪತ್ರಿಕೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಇಂಟರ್ನೆಟ್ ಸುದ್ದಿ ಮೂಲಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುವ ಸಮೂಹ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳು-ಇವೆಲ್ಲವೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಚರ್ಚೆ, ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಪ್ರಸಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯದ ಮೇಲೆ ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ ಪ್ರಭಾವವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿವೆ. ಹೀಗಾಗಿ, ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಆಡಳಿತದ ಮೇಲೆ ಚರ್ಚೆಯ ಕಾರ್ಯವಿಧಾನಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅವುಗಳ ಸಂಭವನೀಯ ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ಸಂಶೋಧನೆ ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಿದೆ.

ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ನಾಲ್ಕನೇ ಆಧಾರಸ್ತಂಭವಾಗಿ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ: ನಾಲ್ಕನೇ ಎಸ್ಕೇಟ್ ಆಗಿ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಕಾರ್ಯವು ಬಹಿಷ್ಕಾರವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಮೇಲೆ ಕಾವಲುಗಾರನಾಗಿ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ, ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಸಂವಾದವನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಚೌಕಟ್ಟಿನೊಳಗೆ ವಿಷಯಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ಹಲವಾರು ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತಪಡಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮೂಹ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಕಾರ್ಯವು ವಿದ್ವಾಂಸರು, ನೀತಿ ನಿರೂಪಕರು ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯಕರ್ತರಿಂದ ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ ಗಮನವನ್ನು ಸೆಳೆದಿದೆ. ವೃತ್ತಪತ್ರಿಕೆಗಳು, ರೇಡಿಯೋ, ದೂರದರ್ಶನ ಮತ್ತು ಆನ್‌ಲೈನ್ ಸುದ್ದಿ ಮೂಲಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುವ ಸಮೂಹ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನಾಯಕರ ಆಶ್ವಾಸನೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಂಚಿಕೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ದೊಡ್ಡ ಪ್ರಭಾವವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿವೆ. ಪರಿಣಾಮವಾಗಿ, ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಆಡಳಿತದ ಮೇಲೆ ಚರ್ಚೆಯ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅವುಗಳ ಸಂಭಾವ್ಯ ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಭಾಷಣೆಗಳು ಮುಂದುವರಿಯುತ್ತವೆ.

ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಸಮೂಹ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ:

"ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ" ಎಂಬ ಪದವು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುವುದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಚರ್ಚೆ ಮತ್ತು ನಿರ್ಧಾರ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರನ್ನು ಸಕ್ರಿಯವಾಗಿ ಒಳಗೊಳ್ಳುವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯನ್ನು ವಿವರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ವಿವಿಧ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ವಿಮರ್ಶಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡುವ ವಿಚಾರಶೀಲ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ನಿರ್ಣಾಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಅವು ವಿದ್ಯಾವಂತ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯವನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುತ್ತವೆ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತಮ ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯುಳ್ಳ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವಲ್ಲಿ ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತವೆ. ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಭಾಷಣವನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಸುಲಭಗೊಳಿಸಿ, ಈ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳು ಅಧಿಕಾರದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡುತ್ತವೆ. ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸಿ, ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರ ಮುಂದೆ ವಿಷಯಗಳನ್ನು ತರುವ ಮೂಲಕ, ಸರ್ಕಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಕಾಪಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ವಿಚಾರಶೀಲ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳು ಅತ್ಯಗತ್ಯ.

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಪ್ರಗತಿ:

ವಿಶ್ವದಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಅತಿ ದೊಡ್ಡ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾದ ಭಾರತವು ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ವಿಚಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹದಾಯಕ ಇತಿಹಾಸವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಕಾರ್ಯವಿಧಾನದ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಲು ಬಂದಾಗ ಭಾರತವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಯಶಸ್ಸಿನ ಕಥೆ ಎಂದು ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ (ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ನಿಯಮಿತವಾಗಿ ಮುಕ್ತ ಮತ್ತು ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ

ಬಡ ಮತ್ತು ಅಂಚಿನಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಗುಂಪುಗಳಿಂದ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿದ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ, ಶಾಂತಿಯುತ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ವರ್ಗಾವಣೆ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ನಡೆಯುತ್ತವೆ). ಭಾರತವು ಕ್ರಿಸ್ತಪೂರ್ವ ಐದನೇ ಶತಮಾನದಷ್ಟು ಹಿಂದಿನ ವೈಚಾರಿಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಸುದೀರ್ಘ ಇತಿಹಾಸವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದರೂ ಸಹ, 1992 ರಲ್ಲಿ 73 ಮತ್ತು 74 ನೇ ಸಾಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಗಳನ್ನು ಅಂಗೀಕರಿಸುವವರೆಗೆ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ಮುನ್ನಡೆಸಲು ಸಾಂಸ್ಥಿಕ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನವು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿಲ್ಲ.

ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸಭೆಯ ರಚನೆಯು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಾಗಿದೆ, ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ 73 ನೇ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯಿದೆಯ ಪರಿಣಾಮವಾಗಿ, ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸಭೆಯು ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಯಾಗಿ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಗ್ರಾಮ ಮಂಡಳಿಯು ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಮತ್ತು ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಲು ಭಾರತದ ದಿಟ್ಟ ಮತ್ತು ಸೃಜನಶೀಲ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನವಾಗಿದೆ. ಹೊಸ ಮೂರು ಹಂತದ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯು ಗ್ರಾಮ ಸಭೆಗೆ ಚರ್ಚೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗಾಗಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಚರ್ಚಿಸುವ ಮತ್ತು ಅನುಮೋದಿಸುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡುವುದರ ಮೂಲಕ ನಾಗರಿಕರ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ಸಾಂಸ್ಥಿಕಗೊಳಿಸಿತು.

ನೀತಿ ರಚನೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಪ್ರಭಾವ:

ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಸಂಭಾಷಣೆಗಾಗಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಸೂಚಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿಸುವುದು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ನೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಾಗಿದೆ. ನೀತಿ ನಿರೂಪಕರು ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ಒತ್ತು ನೀಡಲು ಮತ್ತು ಆದ್ಯತೆ ನೀಡಲು ಆಯ್ಕೆಮಾಡುವ ವಿಷಯಗಳಿಂದ ಪ್ರಭಾವಿತರಾಗುತ್ತಾರೆ, ಇದು ಅವರ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯ ಗ್ರಹಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ವಿಷಯಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಗಮನಕ್ಕೆ ಬಾರದೆ ಹೋಗಬಹುದಾದ ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳತ್ತ ಗಮನ ಸೆಳೆಯುವ ಶಕ್ತಿ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಕ್ಕೆ ಇದೆ. ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರ ಗ್ರಹಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತಪಡಿಸುವುದನ್ನು ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಚೌಕಟ್ಟು ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಸುದ್ದಿ ಲೇಖನಗಳ ರಚನೆಯು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರ ವರ್ತನೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುವ ಶಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ, ಇದು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರ ಬೆಂಬಲ ಅಥವಾ ಉಪಕ್ರಮಗಳಿಗೆ ವಿರೋಧವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಭಾವಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಸಂಸದರು ಅಥವಾ ಶಾಸಕರು ಆಗಾಗ್ಗೆ ಜನಪ್ರಿಯ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯವನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸುವುದರಿಂದ ನೀತಿಗಳು ಹೇಗೆ ಹೊರಹೊಮ್ಮುತ್ತವೆ ಎಂಬುದರ ಮೇಲೆ ಇದು ದೊಡ್ಡ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರಬಹುದು. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಪಾತ್ರ ಹೆಣೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಕಾವಲುಗಾರನಾಗಿ, ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ನೀತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳನ್ನು ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರ, ಅಸಮರ್ಥತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅಧಿಕಾರ ದುರುಪಯೋಗವನ್ನು ಬಹಿರಂಗಪಡಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ, ತನಿಖಾ ಪತ್ರಿಕೋದ್ಯಮವು ಸರ್ಕಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಮುಕ್ತತೆಯನ್ನು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಪಾತ್ರ ಬಹುಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಕ್ರಮಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರಿಗೆ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತದೆ, ವಿವಿಧ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಭಾಷಣಕ್ಕೆ ಸ್ಥಳವನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದನ್ನು ಮಾಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ, ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳು ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯುಳ್ಳ ಮತದಾನವನ್ನು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುತ್ತವೆ, ಇದು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಉಳಿಯಲು ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಪತ್ರಿಕಾ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಅತ್ಯಗತ್ಯ ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಅದು ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳು ಮುಕ್ತವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರತೀಕಾರದ ಭಯವಿಲ್ಲದೆ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಲು ಅನುವು ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುತ್ತದೆ. ನೈತಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ನಿಖರವಾದ ವರದಿಗಾರಿಕೆಯು ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಆಡಳಿತದ ಗುಣಮಟ್ಟವನ್ನು ಉತ್ತಮಪಡಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ತನ್ನ ಕಾವಲುಗಾರನ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಲು ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರವಾಗಿರಬೇಕು ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುವ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳು ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅವರಿಗೆ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯುತವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ ಎಂದು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು. ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ವಸ್ತುನಿಷ್ಠತೆ, ನ್ಯಾಯ ಮತ್ತು ನಿಖರತೆಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ವರದಿ ಮಾಡುವ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ನೈತಿಕ ಪತ್ರಿಕೋದ್ಯಮವು ಸತ್ಯ-ಪರಿಶೀಲನೆ, ಸಮತೋಲಿತ ವರದಿಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ಸಂವೇದನಾಶೀಲತೆಯನ್ನು ತಪ್ಪಿಸುವುದನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಮುಖ್ಯಾಂಶಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚುವರಿಯಾಗಿ ಸಂದರ್ಭ ಮತ್ತು ಆಳವಾದ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡುವ ಸಮಗ್ರ ಪ್ರಸಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡುವುದು ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಪಕ್ಷಪಾತವು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯವನ್ನು ತಿರುಗಿಸುವ ಮತ್ತು ನೀತಿ ಸಂವಾದಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುವ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ವಿವಿಧ ವಿಚಾರಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನಗಳನ್ನು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು, ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಮಾಲೀಕತ್ವವು ವೈವಿಧ್ಯಮಯವಾಗಿರಬೇಕು ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ವಾಯತ್ತವಾಗಿರಬೇಕು. ವಿವೇಚನಾಶೀಲ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ಅಂತರ್ಗತ, ತಾರ್ಕಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತಮ ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯುಳ್ಳ ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವ ವೇದಿಕೆಗಳಾಗಿವೆ, ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ನಿರ್ಧಾರ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಭಾರತೀಯ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಚೌಕಟ್ಟಿನೊಳಗೆ, ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯವನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ, ನೀತಿಗಳ ರಚನೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ಜಾಗರೂಕತೆಯ ಜನಸಮೂಹವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಚರ್ಚಾ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಕಾರ್ಯವು ನಿರ್ಣಾಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ. ಭಾರತವು ವಿಶ್ವದ ಅತಿದೊಡ್ಡ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಾಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ, ವಿವಿಧ ಗುಂಪುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವಸ್ತುನಿಷ್ಠ ಸಂಭಾಷಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರೋಪಿಸುವ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗೆ ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಪ್ರಬಂಧವು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯದ ಮೇಲೆ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುವ, ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ನೀತಿಯ ರಚನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುವ ಮತ್ತು ತೊಡಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ನಾಗರಿಕ ನಿಶ್ಚಿತಾರ್ಥವನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವ ವಿಧಾನಗಳನ್ನು ವಿಚಾರಣಾ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ತನಿಖೆ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.

ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವುದು

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯವು ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕವಾಗಿ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳಿಂದ ಪ್ರಭಾವಿತವಾಗಿದೆ, ಇದು ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ, ಕಾರ್ಯಸೂಚಿಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ನಿರ್ಣಾಯಕ ವಿಷಯಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸುಗಮಗೊಳಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹತ್ವದ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಆನ್‌ಲೈನ್ ಪ್ಲಾಟ್‌ಫಾರ್ಮ್‌ಗಳು, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸಂವಾದಾತ್ಮಕ ವೇದಿಕೆಗಳಂತಹ ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳ ಆಗಮನದೊಂದಿಗೆ, ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ವಿಕಸನಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಏಕಮುಖ ಸಂವಹನವನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುವ ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಭಿನ್ನವಾಗಿ, ವಿಚಾರಶೀಲ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಸಂವಾದದಲ್ಲಿ ತೊಡಗಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು, ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಬಲ ನಿರೂಪಣೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಸವಾಲು ಹಾಕಲು ಅನುವು ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುತ್ತದೆ.

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ, ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ, ಭಾಷಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ-ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ವೈವಿಧ್ಯತೆಯು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ವಿಘಟಿತ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ, ವಿಚಾರಶೀಲ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಬಹುತ್ವ ಮತ್ತು ಅಂತರ್ಗತ ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಜಾಗವನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಸುದ್ದಿ ಚರ್ಚಾ ಪೋರ್ಟಲ್‌ಗಳು, ಸಮುದಾಯ ರೇಡಿಯೋ ಕೇಂದ್ರಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ವೇದಿಕೆಗಳಂತಹ ವೇದಿಕೆಗಳು ಅಂಚಿನಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಧ್ವನಿಗಳನ್ನು ಕೇಳಲು ಅವಕಾಶಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತವೆ, ಉತ್ಕೃಷ್ಟ ಮತ್ತು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಸಮಗ್ರವಾದ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಪ್ರವಚನಕ್ಕೆ ಕೊಡುಗೆ ನೀಡುತ್ತವೆ. ಹೆಚ್ಚುವರಿಯಾಗಿ, ನಾಗರಿಕರು ತಜ್ಞರು,

ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ನೀತಿ ನಿರೂಪಕರೊಂದಿಗೆ ನೇರವಾಗಿ ತೊಡಗಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದು, ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಕ್ರಿಯಾತ್ಮಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ಪಂದಿಸುವ ವಿಚಾರಗಳ ವಿನಿಮಯವನ್ನು ಸುಗಮಗೊಳಿಸಬಹುದು.

ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ: ಪತ್ರಿಕೆಗಳು, ರೇಡಿಯೋ ಮತ್ತು ದೂರದರ್ಶನ

ಪತ್ರಿಕೆಗಳು, ರೇಡಿಯೋ ಮತ್ತು ದೂರದರ್ಶನದಂತಹ ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ವೇದಿಕೆಗಳು ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸಿವೆ. ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪತ್ರಿಕೆಗಳು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವಿಷಯಗಳ ಆಳವಾದ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತವೆ, ದೂರದರ್ಶನವು ನೈಜ-ಸಮಯದ ಸುದ್ದಿ ಪ್ರಸಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ರೇಡಿಯೋ ಇತರ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳು ಇಲ್ಲದ ದೂರದ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ತಲುಪುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ವೇದಿಕೆಗಳು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅರಿವು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ತತ್ವಗಳ ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ದೀರ್ಘಕಾಲದಿಂದ ಸುಗಮಗೊಳಿಸಿವೆ, ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗೆ ಕಾನೂನಿನ ನಿಯಮ, ನಾಗರಿಕ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಆಡಳಿತ ರಚನೆಗಳು ಮುಂತಾದವುಗಳು.

ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಪ್ರಚಾರಗಳು, ಆನ್‌ಲೈನ್ ಅರ್ಜಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಚಾನೆಲ್‌ಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಪ್ರಾರಂಭಿಸಿದ ತಳಮಟ್ಟದ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲತೆಯು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಹೊಸ ಮಾರ್ಗಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದೆ. ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗೆ, #MeTooIndia ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಸರ ನ್ಯಾಯಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಆಂದೋಲನಗಳಂತಹ ಅಭಿಯಾನಗಳು ಚರ್ಚಾ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವನ್ನು ಸಮರ್ಥನೆ, ಜಾಗೃತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯವನ್ನು ಕ್ರೋಢೀಕರಿಸಲು ವೇದಿಕೆಗಳಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡಿವೆ. ಈ ವೇದಿಕೆಗಳು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ನಾಗರಿಕರ ಧ್ವನಿಯನ್ನು ವರ್ಧಿಸಿದೆ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಸ್ಪಂದಿಸಲು ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಜನಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳನ್ನು ಒತ್ತಾಯಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಇದಲ್ಲದೆ, ನಾಗರಿಕ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಪಾತ್ರ - ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಅವರ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳು, ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಕಾರ್ಯಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ತಿಳಿಸುವುದು-ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ ಜಾಗೃತ ಮತ್ತು ಸಕ್ರಿಯ ನಾಗರಿಕರನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿದೆ. ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳು, ಟಾಕ್ ಶೋಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸಂವಾದಾತ್ಮಕ ಸೆಷನ್‌ಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ, ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ವೇದಿಕೆಗಳು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರಸಾರ ಮಾಡುವುದಲ್ಲದೆ ನಾಗರಿಕ ತೊಡಗಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಸುಗಮಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ, ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ನಾಗರಿಕರನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುತ್ತದೆ, ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಆಡಳಿತ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮುದಾಯ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಕುರಿತಾಗಿ ಕನ್ನಡ ಟಿ.ವಿ. ನ್ಯೂಸ್ ಚಾನೆಲ್‌ಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಸಾರವಾದ ಕೆಲವು ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳ ಪಟ್ಟಿಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ.

ಕ್ರ.ಸಂ.	ಕನ್ನಡ ನ್ಯೂಸ್ ಚಾನೆಲ್	ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮದ ಶೀರ್ಷಿಕೆ	ಪ್ರಸಾರವಾದ ದಿನಾಂಕ	ವೀಕ್ಷಕರ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ	ಅವಧಿ
1	ನ್ಯೂಸ್ ಕನ್ನಡ 18	Talk Tonic ವಿಷಯ: MUDA ಪ್ರಕರಣದ	12/11/2024	79,000	2 ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ
2	ಸುವರ್ಣ ನ್ಯೂಸ್	ಲೆಪ್ಪೆ - ರೈಟ್ - ಸೆಂಟರ್ ವಿಷಯ: ವಕ್ಸ ಜಾಗ ವತ್ತುವರಿ	13/11/2024	125000	1 ದಿನದಲ್ಲಿ
3	ಸುವರ್ಣ ನ್ಯೂಸ್	ಲೆಪ್ಪೆ - ರೈಟ್ - ಸೆಂಟರ್ ವಿಷಯ: "ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ UCC ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆ ಇದೆಯಾ"	ನವಂಬರ್ 2023	2,86,000	1 ವರ್ಷದಲ್ಲಿ

4	ಟಿ.ವಿ. 9 ಕನ್ನಡ	ಚನ್ನಪಟ್ಟಣ ಉಪ ಚುನಾವಣೆ	14/11/2024	1,00,000	6 ಗಂಟೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ
5	ಪಬ್ಲಿಕ್ ಟಿ.ವಿ.	Big Bulletin - ಮುಡಾ ಚಕ್ರವ್ಯೂಹದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಿ.ಎಂ.	13/09/2024	4,97,000	2 ತಿಂಗಳಲ್ಲಿ
6	ಪಬ್ಲಿಕ್ ಟಿ.ವಿ.	ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ೨೦೨೪ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಫಲಿತಾಂಶ	-	10 ಮಿಲಿಯನ್	5 ತಿಂಗಳಲ್ಲಿ

ಕನ್ನಡ ಟಿ.ವಿ. ನ್ಯೂಸ್ ಚ್ಯಾನಲ್ ಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಸಾರವಾದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಸುದ್ದಿಗಳು ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳ ವರ್ತನೆ, ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳ ಹಗರಣಗಳ ಕುರಿತಾದ ಸುದ್ದಿಗಳನ್ನು ಎಷ್ಟರ ಮಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರು ವೀಕ್ಷಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಕೆಲವೇ ಕೆಲವು ನ್ಯೂಸ್ ಚ್ಯಾನೆಲ್‌ಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಸಾರವಾಗುವ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ವಿವರಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದರಿಂದ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗುವ ಅಂಶವೆಂದರೆ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಜನರು ಟಿ.ವಿ. ಸುದ್ದಿ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು, ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳ ನಡವಳಿಕೆಗಳು, ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿ, ಹಗರಣಗಳು ಇವುಗಳನ್ನೆಲ್ಲಾ ಕಾಳಜಿಯಿಂದ ವೀಕ್ಷಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದು, ಅವುಗಳಿಗೆ ಚಾಟ್ ಬಾಕ್ಸ್ ಮೂಲಕ ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ರಿಯೆಯನ್ನೂ ಕೂಡ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಟಿ.ವಿ. ಸುದ್ದಿಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳು ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತದೆ.

ಅಂತರ್ಗತ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಸಕ್ರಿಯಗೊಳಿಸಲಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ

ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅಂತರ್ಗತ ಪಾಲ್ಗೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಸಕ್ರಿಯಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವು ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಾಗಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಲು, ಎಲ್ಲಾ ನಾಗರಿಕರು, ಅವರ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ-ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಸ್ಥಿತಿ, ಲಿಂಗ ಅಥವಾ ಜನಾಂಗೀಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಲೆಕ್ಕಿಸದೆ, ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ಪ್ರವೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಚರ್ಚೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವ ಅವಕಾಶವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವುದು ಅತ್ಯಗತ್ಯ.

ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಖಾತರಿಪಡಿಸುವುದು

ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡುವಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಚಾರಶೀಲ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಯ ವಿಷಯಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ತನಿಖೆ ಮತ್ತು ವರದಿ ಮಾಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ, ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ಕಾವಲುಗಾರನಾಗಿ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ, ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರ, ಅಸಮರ್ಥತೆ ಅಥವಾ ಅಧಿಕಾರದ ದುರುಪಯೋಗವನ್ನು ಬಹಿರಂಗಪಡಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಕೇಸ್ ಸ್ಟಡಿ:

1. ವಾಲ್ಮೀಕಿ ಕಾರ್ಪೊರೇಷನ್ ಹಗರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಅದರ ನಂತರದ ವ್ಯಾಪಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಪ್ರಸಾರದ ನಂತರ:-

ಮಹರ್ಷಿ ವಾಲ್ಮೀಕಿ ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡಗಳ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ನಿಗಮದ ಹಗರಣವನ್ನು ಕನ್ನಡದ ಎಲ್ಲ ಟಿ.ವಿ. ನ್ಯೂಸ್ ಚ್ಯಾನೆಲ್‌ಗಳು ನಿರಂತರವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಸಾರ ಮಾಡಿವೆ. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಇಬ್ಬರು ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳನ್ನು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಅಮಾನತುಗೊಳಿಸಿದೆ. ₹ 90 ಕೋಟಿಗೂ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಮೊತ್ತದ ಅನುಮೋದಿತ ವರ್ಗಾವಣೆ ಕುರಿತು ಮೃತ ಸಹೋದ್ಯೋಗಿಯೊಬ್ಬರು ಬರೆದಿರುವ ಟಿಪ್ಪಣಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳು ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದ ಸಮೂಹ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳಿಂದ ಮುಜುಗರಕ್ಕೊಳಗಾದ ಶ್ರೀ ನಾಗೇಂದ್ರ, ವಾಲ್ಮೀಕಿ ನಿಗಮ ಮಂಡಳಿಯ ಅಧ್ಯಕ್ಷರು, ಇವರು ರಾಜೀನಾಮೆ ನೀಡುವಂತಾಯಿತು.

2. 2022ರಲ್ಲಿ ಅಂದಿನ ಬಿ.ಜಿ.ಪಿ. ಸರ್ಕಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣಾಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಚಿವರಾಗಿದ್ದ ಕೆ.ಎಸ್.ಈಶ್ವರಪ್ಪ ಅವರು ಗುತ್ತಿಗೆದಾರರಿಂದ ಶೇ.40ರಷ್ಟು ಕಮಿಷನ್ ಪಡೆದಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂದು ಆರೋಪಿಸಲಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಗುತ್ತಿಗೆದಾರರೊಬ್ಬರು ಆತ್ಮಹತ್ಯೆಗೆ ಶರಣಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಟಿ.ವಿ. ನ್ಯೂಸ್ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳ ನಿರಂತರ ಪ್ರಸಾರದಿಂದಾಗಿ ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಸಚಿವರ ರಾಜೀನಾಮೆಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಬೇಕಾಯಿತು.

3. ನಿರ್ಭಯಾ ಪ್ರಕರಣ:

ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಮಟ್ಟದ ಸುದ್ದಿ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳ ಪ್ರಭಾವವನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸುವುದಾದರೆ; ನಿರ್ಭಯಾ ಪ್ರಕರಣ, ಇದನ್ನು "ದೆಹಲಿ ಗ್ಯಾಂಗ್ ರೇಪ್" ಪ್ರಕರಣ ಎಂದೂ ಕರೆಯಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಡಿಸೆಂಬರ್ 16, 2012 ರಂದು ಓರ್ವ ಮಹಿಳೆಯನ್ನು ಆರು ಜನರು ಸಾಮೂಹಿಕ ಅತ್ಯಾಚಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಕಿರುಕುಳ ನೀಡಿದರು. ಚಲಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದ ಬಸ್ಸಿನೊಳಗೆ ಹಲ್ಲೆ ನಡೆದಿದೆ. ಹದಿಮೂರು ದಿನಗಳ ನಂತರ ಅವಳು ತೀರಿಕೊಂಡಳು. ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳು ಈ ಭಯಾನಕ ಘಟನೆಯನ್ನು ಹಲವಾರು ತಿಂಗಳುಗಳ ಕಾಲ ಮತ್ತು ಒಳ್ಳೆಯ ಕಾರಣಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯಿಂದ ವರದಿ ಮಾಡಿದವು. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಈ ಪ್ರಕರಣವು ದೊಡ್ಡ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಆಂದೋಲನಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಯಿತು.

ತಪ್ಪು ಮಾಹಿತಿ, ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಪಕ್ಷಪಾತ, ಮತ್ತು ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಡಿವೈಡ್ :

ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರು, ನಿರ್ಧಾರ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವವರು ಮತ್ತು ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳ ನಡುವಿನ ಮುಕ್ತ, ತಾರ್ಕಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತಮ ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯುಳ್ಳ ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳಿಂದ ವಿಚಾರಾತ್ಮಕ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಪ್ರಯೋಜನ ಪಡೆಯುತ್ತವೆ. ಆದಾಗ್ಯೂ, ತಪ್ಪು ಮಾಹಿತಿ, ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಪಕ್ಷಪಾತ ಮತ್ತು ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ವಿಭಜನೆಯು ಈ ಕಾರ್ಯವಿಧಾನಗಳಿಗೆ ಗಂಭೀರ ಅಡೆತಡೆಗಳನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಂಭಾಷಣೆಯ ವಿಶ್ವಾಸಾರ್ಹತೆಯನ್ನು ಅಪಾಯಕ್ಕೆ ತಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ, ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ನಿಶ್ಚಿತಾರ್ಥದ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಸಂಕುಚಿತಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಆಡಳಿತ ರಚನೆಗಳ ನ್ಯಾಯಸಮ್ಮತತೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರಶ್ನಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಮತ್ತು ಚರ್ಚೆಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಮೇಲೆ ಹೇಗೆ ಪರಿಣಾಮ ಬೀರುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

1. ತಪ್ಪು ಮತ್ತು ತಪ್ಪುದಾರಿಗಳೆರಡು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯು ತಪ್ಪು ಅಥವಾ ತಪ್ಪುದಾರಿಗಳೆರಡು ವಿಷಯದ ಉದ್ದೇಶಪೂರ್ವಕ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿತರಣೆಯಾಗಿದೆ, ಆದರೆ ತಪ್ಪು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯು ಅಂತಹ ವಿಷಯವನ್ನು ಉದ್ದೇಶಪೂರ್ವಕವಲ್ಲದ ಹರಡುವಿಕೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಎರಡೂ ವಿಚಾರಣಾ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳ ಸಮಗ್ರತೆಗೆ ಗಣನೀಯ ಬೆದರಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಒಡ್ಡುತ್ತವೆ, ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ, ಮಾಹಿತಿಯು ಬಹು ವೇದಿಕೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವೇಗವಾಗಿ ಹರಿಯುತ್ತದೆ.

ತಪ್ಪಾದ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ರಿಯಿಸಲು ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಒತ್ತಡವನ್ನು ಉಂಟುಮಾಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ತಪ್ಪು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯು ನೀತಿ-ನಿರೂಪಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಋಣಾತ್ಮಕ ಪರಿಣಾಮ ಬೀರುತ್ತದೆ. ನೀತಿ ನಿರೂಪಕರು ಕಾನೂನುಬದ್ಧ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಕಾಳಜಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ತಪ್ಪು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯಿಂದ ಉತ್ತೇಜಿತವಾದ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಗಳ ನಡುವಿನ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸವನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸಬಹುದು, ಇದು ನೈಜ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸದಿರುವ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯಿಲ್ಲದ ನೀತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ತಪ್ಪು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯು ಅನಿಯಂತ್ರಿತವಾಗಿ ಹರಡುವ ಪರಿಸರದಲ್ಲಿ, ತರ್ಕಬದ್ಧ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಕ್ಷ್ಯಾಧಾರಿತ ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳನ್ನು ಭಾವನಾತ್ಮಕವಾಗಿ ಆವೇಶದ ಮತ್ತು ಆಗಾಗ್ಗೆ ತಪ್ಪುದಾರಿಗಳೆರಡು ನಿರೂಪಣೆಗಳಿಂದ ಬದಲಾಯಿಸಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಪರಿಹಾರಗಳು:

- **ಸತ್ಯ-ಪರಿಶೀಲನೆಯ ಉಪಕ್ರಮಗಳು:** ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ಸತ್ಯ-ಪರಿಶೀಲನಾ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು ಸುದ್ದಿಯ ಸತ್ಯಾಸತ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸರಿಪಡಿಸುವ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ತಪ್ಪು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸಬಹುದು.
- **ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತಾ ಅಭಿಯಾನಗಳು:** ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ಮೂಲಗಳನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ವಿಮರ್ಶಾತ್ಮಕವಾಗಿ ಮೌಲ್ಯಮಾಪನ ಮಾಡುವುದು, ಸುಳ್ಳು ಸುದ್ದಿಗಳನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ಸತ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಕ್ರಾಸ್-ಚೆಕ್ ಮಾಡುವುದು ಹೇಗೆ ಎಂಬ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರಿಗೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ನೀಡುವುದು ತಪ್ಪು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಪಾಪಕತ್ವವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸಬಹುದು.
- **ಪ್ಲಾಟ್‌ಫಾರ್ಮ್ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆ:** ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಕಂಪನಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಪ್ಲಾಟ್‌ಫಾರ್ಮ್‌ಗಳು ವಿಶ್ವಾಸಾರ್ಹ ಮೂಲಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಚಾರ ಮಾಡುವಾಗ ಸುಳ್ಳು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ಹರಡುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡುವ ತಂತ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.

ವಿಮರ್ಶಾತ್ಮಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಮಾಪನ:

ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಖಾತ್ರಿಪಡಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ, ನಾಗರಿಕ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ, ವಿದ್ಯಾವಂತ ಪೌರತ್ವವನ್ನು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಮತ್ತು ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವ ಆಡಳಿತವನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ, ವಿಚಾರಶೀಲ ಚರ್ಚಾತ್ಮಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ಭಾರತೀಯ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ಬಲಪಡಿಸುವ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಎರಡೂ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಅತ್ಯಗತ್ಯ, ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಅದು ಜನರಿಗೆ ಧ್ವನಿಯನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ, ನೀತಿಯನ್ನು ಚರ್ಚಿಸಲು ಅವರಿಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅದರ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.

ಆದರೆ ಭಾರತೀಯ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಪ್ರಗತಿಗೆ ವಿಚಾರಶೀಲ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ಗಣನೀಯ ಕೊಡುಗೆ ನೀಡಲು, ಸುಳ್ಳು ಮಾಹಿತಿ, ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಪಕ್ಷಪಾತ ಮತ್ತು ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಅಂತರದಂತಹ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ. ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಒಳಗೊಳ್ಳುವ, ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯುಳ್ಳ ಮತ್ತು ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯುತವಾದ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಲು, ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯವನ್ನು ರಕ್ಷಿಸಲು, ಸತ್ಯ-ಆಧಾರಿತ ವರದಿಯನ್ನು ಬೆಂಬಲಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಇಂಟರ್ನೆಟ್ ಪ್ರವೇಶವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಲು ಇದು ಅತ್ಯಗತ್ಯವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಭಾರತೀಯ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಮೂಲ ತತ್ವಗಳನ್ನು ಕಾಪಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಮತ್ತು ಬಲಪಡಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಚಾರಶೀಲ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮವು ಅತ್ಯಗತ್ಯವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ.

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ಪೀಠಿಕೆ:

Social justice, in contemporary politics, social science, and political philosophy, the fair treatment and equitable status of all individuals and social groups within a state or society.

ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯವೆಂದರೆ ಕೇವಲ ಹಿಂದಿನ ಚಿಂತನೆಯಿಂದರೆ ಸಾಲದು, ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದ ಕೃತಿಗಳು ಕೇವಲ ಇತಿಹಾಸದ ಉತ್ಪನ್ನಗಳಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸಿದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಭೌತಿಕ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಗಳನ್ನು ನೋಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸಬಹುದು. ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸನ ಬಂಡವಾಳವಾದವು ಹೇಳುವಂತೆ "ಭೌತಿಕ ಜೀವನದ ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ವಿಧಾನವು ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆಯಾಗಿ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಬೌದ್ಧಿಕ ಜೀವನ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತ ಕಾರ್ಲ್ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸನಿಂದ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ವಲ್ಪ ಮಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಫ್ರೆಡ್ರಿಕ್ ಎಂಗೆಲ್ಸ್‌ನಿಂದ 19 ನೇ ಶತಮಾನದ ಮಧ್ಯಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಪಡಿಸಿದ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತದ ಒಂದು ಭಾಗ .ಇದು ಮೂಲತಃ 3 ಸಂಬಂಧಿತ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನೊಳಗೊಂಡಿತ್ತು ತಾತ್ವಿಕ ಮಾನವಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಇತಿಹಾಸದ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮ .ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸವಾದವೂ ಕೂಡ ಇದೆ, ಇದನ್ನು ವಿವಿಧ ಚಿಂತಕರು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡು ಅಭ್ಯಾಸ ಮಾಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ.ಸಮಾಜವಾದಿ ಚಳುವಳಿಗಳು, ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ 1914 ಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಮೊದಲು ಆರಂಭ ವಾಗಿದ್ದು,ನಂತರ ಸೋವಿಯತ್ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸವಾದವು ವ್ಲಾಡಿಮಿರ್ ಇಲಿಚ್ ಲೆನಿನ್‌ನಿಂದ ಪರಿಚಯ ಮಾಡಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿದೆ. ಹಾಗೂ ಜೋಸೆಫ್ ಸ್ಟಾಲಿನ್‌ನಿಂದ ಮಾರ್ಪಡಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿದೆ ,ಇದು "ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸಿಸಂ-ಲೆನಿನಿಸಂ" ಎಂಬ ಹೆಸರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ರಷ್ಯಾದ ಕ್ರಾಂತಿಯ ನಂತರ ಸ್ಥಾಪಿತ ಕಮ್ಯುನಿಸ್ಟ್ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತವಾಯಿತು. 1917 ಸ್ಟಾಲಿನಿಸ್ಟ್-ವಿರೋಧಿ ಲಿಯಾನ್ ಟ್ರಾಟ್ಸ್ಕಿ ಮತ್ತು ಅವರ ಅನುಯಾಯಿಗಳು, ಮಾವೋ ಝೆಡಾಂಗ್ ಅವರ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸವಾದ-ಲೆನಿನಿಸಂನ ಚೀನೀ ರೂಪಾಂತರ ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯ ಜಗತ್ತಿನಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವಿಧ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸವಾದಗಳ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಇದರ ಕವಲುಗಳು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸವಾದವನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿವೆ. ಎರಡನೇ ಮಹಾಯುದ್ಧದ ನಂತರದ ನಾನ್‌ಡಾಗ್ ಮ್ಯಾಟಿಕ್ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸವಾದಗಳು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ ಚಿಂತನೆಯನ್ನು ಆಧುನಿಕ ತತ್ವಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಗಳಿಂದ ಎರವಲು ಪಡೆದಿವೆ. ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಎಡ್ಮಂಡ್ ಹಸ್ಸೆಲ್ ಮತ್ತು ಮಾರ್ಟಿನ್

ಹೈಡ್ರೋಗ್ರಾಫಿಕ್ ಅಪರಿಯ ಆದರೆ ಸಿಗ್ನಲ್ ಫ್ರಾಂಟ್ ಮತ್ತು ಇತರರಿಂದಲೂ ಎರವಲು ಪಡೆದಿವೆ. ಈ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಕರು: ಕಾರ್ಲ್ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಫರ್ಡಿನಾಂಡ್ ಲಸ್ಸಾಲ್, ಜಾರ್ಜ್ ವ್ಯಾಲೆಂಟಿನೋವಿಚ್, ಪ್ಲೇಖಾನೋವ್ ಸಾಲ್ವಡಾರ್, ಅಲೆಂಡೆ ಜೇಮ್ಸ್ ಕೊನೊಲಿ

1. ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣಾತ್ಮಕ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ವಾದ 2. ಆಡುಭಾಷೆಯ ಭೌತವಾದ 3. ಪರಿಷ್ಕರಣವಾದ 4. ಶ್ರಮಜೀವಿಗಳ ಸರ್ವಾಧಿಕಾರ 5. ವರ್ಗರಹಿತ ಸಮಾಜ

ಕಾರ್ಲ್ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಅವರ ಚಿಂತನೆಯನ್ನು ಅಂದರೆ ಲಿಖಿತ ಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ತತ್ವಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ಇಳಿಸಲಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಅವರ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ಚಿಂತನೆ ತತ್ವಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದ ಆಮೂಲಾಗ್ರ ವಿಮರ್ಶೆ ಅಷ್ಟೇ. ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಹೆಗೆಲ್ ಅವರ ಆದರ್ಶವಾದಿ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಮತ್ತು ಎಡ ಮತ್ತು ಬಲ ಹಾಗೂ ನಂತರದ ತತ್ವಗಳನ್ನು ಹೆಗೆಲಿಯನ್ನರು ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದನೆ ಮಾಡಿದರು. ಆದಾಗ್ಯೂ, ಇದು ಕೇವಲ ಆ ತತ್ವಗಳ ನಿರಾಕರಣೆ ಅಲ್ಲ. ತತ್ವಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವು ವಾಸ್ತವವಾಗಬೇಕು ಎಂದು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಘೋಷಿಸಿದರು. ಇನ್ನು ಮುಂದೆ ಜಗತ್ತನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥೈಸುವುದರಲ್ಲಿ ಚಿಂತಕರು ತೃಪ್ತರಾಗಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಿಲ್ಲ; ಒಬ್ಬರು ಅದನ್ನು ಪರಿವರ್ತಿಸುವುದರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಕಾಳಜಿ ವಹಿಸಬೇಕು, ಇದರರ್ಥ ಪ್ರಪಂಚವನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಅದರ ಮಾನವ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆ ಎರಡನ್ನೂ ಪರಿವರ್ತಿಸುವುದು. ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಪ್ರತಿಯಾಗಿ, ವಿಚಾರಗಳ ವಿಮರ್ಶೆಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಅನುಭವದ ವಿಮರ್ಶೆಯ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿತ್ತು. ವಾಸ್ತವವಾಗಿ, ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಜ್ಞಾನವು ವಿಚಾರಗಳ ವಿಮರ್ಶೆಯನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ನಂಬಿದ್ದರು. ಅವರು ಅನುಭವವಾದಿಯಾಗಿರಲಿಲ್ಲ. ಬದಲಿಗೆ, ಅವರ ಕೆಲಸವು ಹೆಗೆಲ್, ಜೋಹಾನ್ ಫಿಚ್, ಇಮ್ಯಾನ್ಯುಯೆಲ್ ಕಾಂಟ್, ಆಡಮ್ ಸ್ಮಿತ್, ಡೇವಿಡ್ ರಿಕಾರ್ಡೋ ಮತ್ತು ಹಿಂದಿನ ತತ್ವಜ್ಞಾನಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅರ್ಥಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಜ್ಞರಿಂದ ಪಡೆದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ (ವಿನಿಯೋಗ, ಅನಿರೀಕರಣ, ಪ್ರಾಕ್ಸಿಸ್, ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಶ್ರಮ, ಮೌಲ್ಯ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ) ಸೇರಿದೆ. ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಿದ್ದು ಸ್ವೆಟ್ ಮಿಲ್. ಮಾನವ ಸ್ವಭಾವ, ಜ್ಞಾನ ಮತ್ತು ವಸ್ತುವಿನಂತಹ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ಗುಂಪಿನ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅಮೂರ್ತ ದೃಢೀಕರಣಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡುವ ಬದಲು, ಅವರು ಇತರರೊಂದಿಗೆ ಅದರ ಕ್ರಿಯಾತ್ಮಕ ಸಂಬಂಧದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಎಲ್ಲಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ವಾಸ್ತವಗಳಿಗೆ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಚಿಂತನೆಯನ್ನು ಅನನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ನಿರೂಪಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ನ್ಯಾಯದ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತಗಳು ಪಶ್ಚಿಮದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಅಧಿಕಾರದ ಮೊದಲ ತಾತ್ವಿಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಗ್ರೀಸ್ ಮತ್ತು ರೋಮ್ನಲ್ಲಿ ಚಿಂತಕರು ಕೈಗೊಂಡರು, ಅವರ ಕೃತಿಗಳು ಸೈದ್ಧಾಂತಿಕ ಊಹಾಪೋಹಗಳನ್ನು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಒಳನೋಟವುಳ್ಳ ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕ ಅವಲೋಕನಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸಂಯೋಜಿಸಿದವು. ಈ ಕೃತಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಪ್ರಭಾವಶಾಲಿಯಾದದ್ದು ಪ್ಲೇಟೋನ ಗಣರಾಜ್ಯ, ಇದು ಸಂವಾದದ ರೂಪದಲ್ಲಿ, ನ್ಯಾಯವನ್ನು ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕ ಸದ್ಗುಣ ಮತ್ತು ಆದರ್ಶ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಿಸುವ ಗುಣಲಕ್ಷಣವಾಗಿ ಸುದೀರ್ಘ ಪರಿಶೀಲನೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಪ್ಲೇಟೋನ ಪ್ರಕಾರ, ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕ ಆತ್ಮದಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ನಗರ-ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿನ ನ್ಯಾಯವು ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದೂ ರೂಪುಗೊಂಡ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಅಂಶಗಳ ಸಾಮರಸ್ಯದ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಚರಣೆಯನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ: ತರ್ಕ, ಆತ್ಮ ಮತ್ತು ಆತ್ಮದಲ್ಲಿನ ಹಸಿವು; ಮತ್ತು ನಗರ-ರಾಜ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಆಡಳಿತಗಾರರು, ರಕ್ಷಕರು ಅಥವಾ ಸೈನಿಕರು ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದಕರು ಉದಾ. ರೈತರು ಮತ್ತು ಕುಶಲಕರ್ಮಿಗಳು. ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಅಂಶವು ತನಗೆ ಸೂಕ್ತವಾದ ವಸ್ತು ಅಥವಾ ಕಾರ್ಯವನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸಿದಾಗ ಅಥವಾ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಿದಾಗ ಮತ್ತು ಇತರ ಅಂಶಗಳ ಸರಿಯಾದ ಅನ್ವೇಷಣೆಗಳು ಅಥವಾ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಹಸ್ತಕ್ಷೇಪ ಮಾಡದಿದ್ದಾಗ ಎರಡೂ ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಮರಸ್ಯದ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಚರಣೆಯನ್ನು ಅರಿತುಕೊಳ್ಳಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ಲೇಟೋನ ನ್ಯಾಯವಂತರ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನವಾಗಿದ್ದರೂ ಅದು ತಾರತ್ಮ್ಯದಿಂದ ಕೂಡಿದೆ.

ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯವೆಂದರೆ ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಎಲ್ಲ ರೀತಿಯ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಯನ್ನು ಹೋಗಲಾಡಿಸಿ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದವರ, ಬಡವರ, ದುರ್ಬಲರ, ತುಳಿತಕ್ಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಶೋಷಣೆಗೆ ಒಳಪಟ್ಟ ಅಸಹಾಯಕರನ್ನು ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕವಾಗಿ, ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕವಾಗಿ ಮೇಲಕ್ಕೆತ್ತಲು ಶಾಸನಗಳನ್ನು, ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಯೋಜನೆಗಳನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸಿ ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸುವುದು. ಮುಂದುವರೆದು ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾವನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನ್ಯಾಯ ದೊರಕಿಸಿಕೊಡುವುದಾಗಿ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸಿದೆ. ಯಾವ ಭೇದವಿಲ್ಲದೆ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ಪ್ರಜೆಗೂ ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳಾದ ಸಮಾನತೆಯ, ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ, ಶೋಷಣೆಯ ವಿರುದ್ಧ, ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ, ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ, ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ, ಸಂವಿಧಾನಾತ್ಮಕ ಪರಿಹಾರದ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದೇ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ಪ್ರಜೆಗೂ ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ.

ನಮ್ಮ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಲಿಂಗಭೇದ ನಿವಾರಣೆಗೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಗತಿ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಹಲವು ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾಪಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 14ರಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆ ಮತ್ತು ಪುರುಷರಿಗೆ ಸಮಾನವಾದ ಕಾನೂನಿನ ರಕ್ಷಣೆಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 18ರಲ್ಲಿ ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ನೌಕರಿ ಅಥವಾ ಯಾವುದೇ ಹುದ್ದೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ತಾರತಮ್ಯ ನೀತಿ ತೋರಬಾರದೆಂದು ನಿರ್ದೇಶಿಸಿದೆ. ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 21ರಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಮಾನವ ಘನತೆಯಿಂದ ಬದುಕುವ ಹಕ್ಕನ್ನು ಕೊಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಮತ್ತು ಪುರುಷರಿಗೆ ಸಮಾನವಾದ ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗಾಗಿ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಯೋಜನೆಗಳನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 51(ಎ)ನಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಗೌರವಕ್ಕೆ ಚ್ಯುತಿ ತರುವ ಆಚರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ತ್ಯಜಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ನಿರ್ದೇಶಿಸಿದೆ. ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 243ರಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೆ ಕಡ್ಡಾಯ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ ಒದಗಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಇವೆಲ್ಲವೂ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯವೇ ದುಡಿಯುವ ವರ್ಗದ ಹಿತವನ್ನು ಕಾಪಾಡುವ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಹಲವಾರು ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾಪಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾದ ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದಗಳೆಂದರೆ **14, 15, 16, 19, 21, 23, 24, 39, 41, 42** ಮತ್ತು ಈ ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದಗಳ ಅನುಸಾರ ದುಡಿಯುವ ವರ್ಗಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಘ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದಕ್ಕೆ, ಸಭೆ ಸೇರುವುದಕ್ಕೆ, ಶಾಂತಿಯುತವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರತಿಭಟಿಸುವುದಕ್ಕೆ, ಧರಣಿ ನಡೆಸಲು, ಮುಷ್ಕರ ಹೂಡಲು ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯವನ್ನು ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಮನುಷ್ಯರ ಮಾರಾಟ ಮತ್ತು ಬಲಾತ್ಕಾರದ ದುಡಿಮೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಿಷೇಧಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. 14 ವರ್ಷಗಳಿಗಿಂತ ಕಡಿಮೆ ವಯಸ್ಸಿನ ಯಾವುದೇ ಮಗುವನ್ನು ಕಾರ್ಖಾನೆ ಅಥವಾ ಗಣಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡಲು ನಿಯೋಜಿಸತಕ್ಕದ್ದಲ್ಲ ಅಥವಾ ಅಪಾಯಕಾರಿಯಾದ ಉದ್ಯೋಗದಲ್ಲಿ ತೊಡಗಿಸತಕ್ಕದ್ದಲ್ಲ. ಪುರುಷರಿಗೂ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೂ ಸಮಾನ ಕೆಲಸಕ್ಕೆ ಸಮಾನ ವೇತನ ನೀಡುವುದು, ಎಲ್ಲರಿಗೂ ಕನಿಷ್ಠ ವೇತನ ನೀಡುವುದು, ಕೈಗಾರಿಕಾ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕರು ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವುದು ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ರಕ್ಷಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಇವೆಲ್ಲವೂ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯದ ಒಂದು ಭಾಗವೇ ಆಗಿದೆ.

ಸಂವಿಧಾನವು ಅಸ್ಪೃಶ್ಯತೆಯ ನಿರ್ಮೂಲನೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅಸ್ಪೃಶ್ಯರ ವಿಮೋಚನೆಗೆ ಹಲವು ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾಪಿಸಿದೆ. ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 15, 16, 17,18 ನೇ ವಿಧಿ ಕಾನೂನಿನ ಮುಂದೆ ಎಲ್ಲರೂ ಸಮಾನರು, ಕಾನೂನಿಗಿಂತ ಯಾರು ಶ್ರೇಷ್ಠರಲ್ಲ ಎಂಬ ಸರ್ವಸಮಾನ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯದ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತವನ್ನು ಸಾರುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ 19, 20 ಮತ್ತು 21ನೇ ವಿಧಿಗಳು ಮುಕ್ತ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯವನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ, ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯವಿಲ್ಲದೆ ಯಾವುದೇ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಸಮಾಜ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿತ್ವದ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಮಾನಸಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಭೌತಿಕ ಪ್ರಗತಿ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಿಲ್ಲ. 19(a) ವಿಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿಸಿರುವ 6 ಮೂಲ ಭೂತ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯಗಳೆಂದರೆ :1. ವಾಕ್ ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ. 2. ಅಸ್ತಿಗಳಿಲ್ಲದೆ ಶಾಂತಿಯುತವಾಗಿ ಒಂದೆಡೆ ಸೇರುವ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ. 3.ಸಂಘ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳನ್ನು ರಚಿಸುವ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ 4. ಭಾರತದಾದ್ಯಂತ ಚಲಿಸುವ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ 5. ಭಾರತದ ಯಾವುದೇ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸಿಸುವ ಮತ್ತು ಖಾಯಂ ನೆಲೆಸುವ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ 6. ಯಾವುದೇ ವೃತ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವ, ಅಥವಾ ಯಾವುದೇ ವಾಣಿಜ್ಯ ಅಥವಾ ವ್ಯವಹಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ತೊಡಗುವ ಹಕ್ಕು ಮತ್ತು ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಮೊದಲ ಪುಟದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವರಿಸಿದೆ. ಭಾರತದ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳಾದ ನಾವು, ಭಾರತವನ್ನು ಒಂದು ಸಾರ್ವಭೌಮ ಸಮಾಜವಾದಿ ಜಾತ್ಯಾತೀತ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಗಣರಾಜ್ಯವೆಂದು ಘೋಷಿಸುತ್ತಾ ದೃಢಮನಸ್ಸಿನಿಂದ ವಿಧಿಯುಕ್ತವಾಗಿ ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಿ, ಅದರ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳನ್ನು ಖಾತರಿಪಡಿಸಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ: **ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನ್ಯಾಯ**;ವಿಚಾರ, ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ, ನಂಬಿಕೆ, ಭಕ್ತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಆರಾಧನೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ; ಸ್ವಾನಮಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಅವಕಾಶಗಳ ಸಮಾನತೆ, ಮತ್ತು ಅದನ್ನು ಎಲ್ಲರಿಗೂ ಹಂಚುವುದು;ಗಳನ್ನು ದೊರಕಿಸಿ,

ವೈಯುಕ್ತಿಕಘನತೆಮತ್ತುದೇಶದಸಮಗ್ರತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಐಕ್ಯತೆಗೆ ಎಲ್ಲರಲ್ಲೂ ಸಹೋದರತ್ವ ಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸಲು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸಿ; ನಮ್ಮ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ರಚನಾಸಭೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ೧೯೪೯ರ ನವೆಂಬರ್ ಮಾಹೆಯ ೨೬ನೇ ದಿನದಂದು, ನಾವಾಗಿ ನಾವೇ ಈ ಸಂವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು, ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಿ, ನಾವಾಗಿಯೇ ವಿಧಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತೇವೆ ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದರಚನೆಯ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವರಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ವಿಶ್ವದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತ ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಕರಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾರ್ಲ್ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್, ಡಾ. ಬಿ.ಆರ್. ಅಂಬೇಡ್ಕರ್,ಜವಾಹರ ಲಾಲ್ ನೆಹರು, ಜೋಸೆಫ್ ಶುಂಪೀಟರ್, ರಾಜರಾಂ ಮೋಹನ್ ರಾಯ್, ಮೊದಲಾದವರನ್ನು ನೆನೆಯುತ್ತೇವೆ.

ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಭೌತಿಕವಾದವು 1859 ರಲ್ಲಿ, ಅವರ ಜುರ್ ಕೃತಿಕ ಡೆರ್ ಪೊಲಿಟಿಸ್ಕನ್ ಒಕೊನೊಮಿಯ ಮುನ್ನುಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಆರ್ಥಿಕತೆ ವಿಮರ್ಶೆಗೆ ಕೊಡುಗೆ ಸಮಾಜದ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆಗೆ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿ ಅವರಿಗೆ ಸೇವೆ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿದ ಊಹೆಯನ್ನು ಸಂಕ್ಷಿಪ್ತವಾಗಿ ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನಂತೆ ರೂಪಿಸಬಹುದು ಎಂದು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಬರೆದರು. ಪುರುಷರು ನಡೆಸುವ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ, ಅವರು ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಅವರ ಇಚ್ಛೆಯಿಂದ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರವಾದ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರವೇಶಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ, ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ವಸ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ಒಂದು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಹಂತಕ್ಕೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಈ ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳ ಒಟ್ಟು ಮೊತ್ತ ಸಮಾಜದ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಚನೆಯನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುತ್ತದೆ,ಇದೇ ನಿಜವಾದ ಅಡಿಪಾಯ,ಅದರ ಮೇಲೆ ಕಾನೂನು ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮೇಲ್ವಿಚಾರ ಉದ್ಭವಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ರೂಪಗಳಿಗೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಭೌತಿಕ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ವಿಧಾನ ಜೀವನದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಬೌದ್ಧಿಕ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಸ್ವರೂಪವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಅವರ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುವುದು ಪುರುಷರ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯಲ್ಲ; ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ಅವರ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವು ಅವರ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಕಾನೂನಿನ ಮಟ್ಟಕ್ಕೆ ಬೆಳೆದ, ಈ ಊಹೆಯನ್ನು ತರುವಾಯ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಭೌತಿಕ ವಾದ ಎನ್ನಲಾಯಿತು.ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಅದನ್ನು

ಅನ್ವಯಿಸಿದರು.ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ತನ್ನ ಕಾರ್ಯಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತವನ್ನು ಹಲ ವರ್ಷಗಳವರೆಗೆ ಪ್ರತಿಬಿಂಬಿಸಿದರೂ, ಅವನು ಅದನ್ನು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ನಿಖರವಾದ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ರೂಪಿಸಲಿಲ್ಲ:ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಒಂದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ನೈಜತೆಗಳಿಂದಾಗಿ ಅವನಿಗೆ ಸರಿ ಅನ್ನಿಸಿ ದವು.ಅಂದರೆ ಒಬ್ಬರು ಅದರ ಸಾರವನ್ನು ಅಕ್ಷರಶಃ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಂಡರೆ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ವಾಸ್ತವವು ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಚನೆಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ: ಸಮಾಜದ ನಿಜವಾದ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿ ಎಲ್ಲವನ್ನೂ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿರಿಸುವುದು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಚನೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ರಚನೆಯು "ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ವಸ್ತು ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳು", ಅಂದರೆ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆ "ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳು" ಅಥವಾ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿತರಣೆಯನ್ನುನಿಯಂತ್ರಿಸುವ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ "ವಸ್ತು ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳು"ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯ "ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ಪತ್ರವ್ಯವಹಾರವಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಹೇಳಿದ್ದರೂ, ಪತ್ರವ್ಯವಹಾರದ ಸ್ವರೂಪದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅವರು ಎಂದಿಗೂ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸಲಿಲ್ಲ,ಇದು ಅವರ ನಡುವಿನ ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಗಳಿಗೆ ಮೂಲವಾಗಿದೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳು ವಿಧಿ ೧೨ ರಿಂದ ೩೫ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯನೀತಿ ನಿರ್ದೇಶಕ ತತ್ವಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಧಿ ೩೬ ರಿಂದ ೫೧ ಮೂಲ ಭೂತ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ ನಿಚ್ಚಳವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾಪಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಭೌತಿಕವಾದವು 1859 ರಲ್ಲಿ, ಅವರ ಜುರ್ ಕೃತಿಕ ಡೆರ್ ಪೊಲಿಟಿಸ್ಕನ್ ಒಕೊನೊಮಿಯ ಮುನ್ನುಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ (ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಆರ್ಥಿಕತೆ ವಿಮರ್ಶೆಗೆ ಕೊಡುಗೆ) ಸಮಾಜದ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆಗೆ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿ ಅವರಿಗೆ ಸೇವೆ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿದ ಊಹೆಯನ್ನು ಸಂಕ್ಷಿಪ್ತವಾಗಿ ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನಂತೆ ರೂಪಿಸಬಹುದು ಎಂದು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಬರೆದರು. ಪುರುಷರ ನಡೆಸುವ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ, ಅವರು ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಅವರ ಇಚ್ಛೆಯಿಂದ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರವಾದ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರವೇಶಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ, ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ವಸ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ಒಂದು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಹಂತಕ್ಕೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಈ ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳ ಒಟ್ಟು ಮೊತ್ತ ಸಮಾಜದ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಚನೆಯನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುತ್ತದೆ,ಇದೇ ನಿಜವಾದ ಅಡಿಪಾಯ,ಅದರ ಮೇಲೆ ಕಾನೂನು ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮೇಲ್ವಿಚಾರ ಉದ್ಭವಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ರೂಪಗಳಿಗೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಭೌತಿಕ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ವಿಧಾನ ಜೀವನದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಬೌದ್ಧಿಕ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಸ್ವರೂಪವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಅವರ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುವುದು ಪುರುಷರ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯಲ್ಲ; ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ಅವರ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವು ಅವರ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಕಾನೂನಿನ ಮಟ್ಟಕ್ಕೆ ಬೆಳೆದ, ಈ ಊಹೆಯನ್ನು ತರುವಾಯ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಭೌತಿಕ ವಾದ ಎನ್ನಲಾಯಿತು.ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಅದನ್ನು ಅನ್ವಯಿಸಿದರು.ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ತನ್ನ ಕಾರ್ಯಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತವನ್ನು ಹಲ ವರ್ಷಗಳವರೆಗೆ ಪ್ರತಿಬಿಂಬಿಸಿದರೂ, ಅವನು ಅದನ್ನು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ನಿಖರವಾದ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ರೂಪಿಸಲಿಲ್ಲ:ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಒಂದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ನೈಜತೆಗಳಿಂದಾಗಿ ಅವನಿಗೆ ಸರಿ ಅನ್ನಿಸಿ ದವು.ಅಂದರೆ ಒಬ್ಬರು ಅದರ ಸಾರವನ್ನು ಅಕ್ಷರಶಃ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಂಡರೆ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ವಾಸ್ತವವು ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಚನೆಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ: ಸಮಾಜದ ನಿಜವಾದ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿ ಎಲ್ಲವನ್ನೂ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿರಿಸುವುದು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಚನೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ರಚನೆಯು "ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ವಸ್ತು ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳು", ಅಂದರೆ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆ "ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳು" ಅಥವಾ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿತರಣೆಯನ್ನುನಿಯಂತ್ರಿಸುವ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ "ವಸ್ತು ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳು"ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯ "ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ಪತ್ರವ್ಯವಹಾರವಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಹೇಳಿದ್ದರೂ, ಪತ್ರವ್ಯವಹಾರದ ಸ್ವರೂಪದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅವರು ಎಂದಿಗೂ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸಲಿಲ್ಲ,ಇದು ಅವರ ನಡುವಿನ ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಗಳಿಗೆ ಮೂಲವಾಗಿದೆ.

23, 43, 45, 46, 243, 330, 332, 335, 338, 340, 341 ಮತ್ತು 342. ಈ ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದಗಳ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಧರ್ಮ, ಜನಾಂಗ, ಜಾತಿ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಯಾವುದೇ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಸ್ಥಳಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರ್ಬಂಧಿಸುವಂತಿಲ್ಲ; ಎಲ್ಲರಿಗೂ ಸಮಾನ ಅವಕಾಶಗಳನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸಬೇಕು, ಸಮಾನತೆಯ ಹಕ್ಕು (೧೪ ರಿಂದ ೧೮) ಯಾರಿಗೂ ಯಾವುದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ತಾರತಮ್ಯ ತೋರುವಂತಿಲ್ಲ. ೧೭ನೇ ವಿಧಿಯ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಅಸ್ಪೃಶ್ಯತೆಯ ಆಚರಣೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷಾರ್ಹ ಅಪರಾಧವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಇವರ ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ವೃದ್ಧಿಗೊಳಿಸಲು ವಿಶೇಷ ಕ್ರಮ ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು ಮತ್ತು ಎಲ್ಲಾ ರೀತಿಯ ಶೋಷಣೆಯಿಂದ ಅವರನ್ನು ರಕ್ಷಿಸತಕ್ಕದ್ದು ಎನ್ನುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದೂ ಸಹ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯವೇ ಆಗಿದೆ. ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿ, ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡ ಹಾಗೂ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ವರ್ಗಗಳಿಗೆ ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ, ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಉದ್ಯೋಗಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯದ ಒಂದು ಸಣ್ಣ ಭಾಗವಷ್ಟೆ. ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯೇ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯವಲ್ಲ. ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯವೆಂದರೆ ಕೇವಲ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯಲ್ಲ. ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯವನ್ನು ವಿಸ್ತರಿಸಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ. ಕೃಷಿ ಬಿಕ್ಕಟ್ಟಿನಿಂದ ರೈತರು ಅತ್ಯಹತ್ಯೆ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಶೇ.90ರಷ್ಟು ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕರು ಅಸಂಘಟಿತ ವಲಯದಲ್ಲಿ ದುಡಿಯುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಶೇ.90ರಷ್ಟು ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕರು ಅಸಂಘಟಿತ ವಲಯದಲ್ಲಿ ದುಡಿಯುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ವಯೋವೃದ್ಧರು ಅನೇಕ ಕಷ್ಟಗಳನ್ನು ಅನುಭವಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ವಿಕಲಚೇತನರು ಸಮಾಜದ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಹಿನಿಗೆ ಬರಲಾಗಿಲ್ಲ, ಅಭಾಗ್ಯ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರನ್ನು ವೇಶ್ಯಾವಾಟಿಕೆಯಿಂದ ಹೊರತರಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗಿಲ್ಲ. ಇಂತಹ ಅನೇಕರ ನೆರವಿಗೆ ಹೋಗುವುದು ಕೂಡ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯವಾಗಬೇಕು. ಭಾರತದ ಅಸಂಘಟಿತ ಕೃಷಿಯೇತರ ವಲಯವು ಅಕ್ಟೋಬರ್ 2022 ರಿಂದ ಸೆಪ್ಟೆಂಬರ್ 2023 ರವರೆಗೆ ಸುಮಾರು 11 ಕೋಟಿ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕರನ್ನು ನೇಮಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದೆ, ಇದು ಆರೋಗ್ಯಕರ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮಾರುಕಟ್ಟೆ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಯನ್ನು ತೋರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ವಲಯದ ವಾರ್ಷಿಕ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಯ ದರವು 7.84% ಆಗಿದ್ದು, ಉದ್ಯೋಗವನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸುವ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವನ್ನು ಪ್ರದರ್ಶಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಹೆಚ್ಚುವರಿಯಾಗಿ, ಒಟ್ಟು ಕಾರ್ಯಪಡೆಯ 57.3% ಸ್ವಯಂ ಉದ್ಯೋಗಿಗಳು, ಮತ್ತು 18.3% ಗೃಹ ಉದ್ಯಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವೇತನರಹಿತ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕರಾಗಿ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಭೌತಿಕವಾದವು 1859 ರಲ್ಲಿ, ಅವರ ಜುರ್ ಕೃತಿಕ್ ಡೆರ್ ಪೊಲಿಟಿಸ್ಸೆನ್ ಒಕೊನೊಮಿಯ ಮುನ್ನುಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ (ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಆರ್ಥಿಕತೆ ವಿಮರ್ಶೆಗೆ ಕೊಡುಗೆ)

ನ್ಯಾಯವು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ.

ಸಮಾಜದ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆಗೆ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿ ಅವರಿಗೆ ಸೇವೆ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿದ ಊಹೆಯನ್ನು ಸಂಕ್ಷಿಪ್ತವಾಗಿ ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನಂತೆ ರೂಪಿಸಬಹುದು ಎಂದು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಬರೆದರು. ಪುರುಷರು ನಡೆಸುವ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ, ಅವರು ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಅವರ ಇಚ್ಛೆಯಿಂದ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರವಾದ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರವೇಶಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ, ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ವಸ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ಒಂದು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಹಂತಕ್ಕೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಈ ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳ ಒಟ್ಟು ಮೊತ್ತ ಸಮಾಜದ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಚನೆಯನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುತ್ತದೆ, ಇದೇ ನಿಜವಾದ ಅಡಿಪಾಯ, ಅದರ ಮೇಲೆ ಕಾನೂನು ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮೇಲ್ವಿಚಾರಣೆ ಉದ್ಭವಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ರೂಪಗಳಿಗೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಭೌತಿಕ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ವಿಧಾನ ಜೀವನದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಬೌದ್ಧಿಕ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಸ್ವರೂಪವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಅವರ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುವುದು ಪುರುಷರ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯಲ್ಲ; ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ಅವರ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವು ಅವರ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಕಾನೂನಿನ ಮಟ್ಟಕ್ಕೆ ಬೆಳೆದ, ಈ ಊಹೆಯನ್ನು ತರುವಾಯ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಭೌತಿಕ ವಾದ ಎನ್ನಲಾಯಿತು. ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಅದನ್ನು ಅನ್ವಯಿಸಿದರು. ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ತನ್ನ ಕಾರ್ಯಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತವನ್ನು ಹಲ ವರ್ಷಗಳವರೆಗೆ ಪ್ರತಿಬಿಂಬಿಸಿದರೂ,

ಅವನು ಅದನ್ನು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ನಿಖರವಾದ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ರೂಪಿಸಲಿಲ್ಲ; ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಒಂದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ನೈಜತೆಗಳಿಂದಾಗಿ ಅವನಿಗೆ ಸರಿ ಅನ್ನಿಸಿ ದವು. ಅಂದರೆ ಒಬ್ಬರು ಅದರ ಸಾರವನ್ನು ಅಕ್ಷರಶಃ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಂಡರೆ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ವಾಸ್ತವವು ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಚನೆಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ: ಸಮಾಜದ ನಿಜವಾದ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿ ಎಲ್ಲವನ್ನೂ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿರಿಸುವುದು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಚನೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ರಚನೆಯು "ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ವಸ್ತು ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳು", ಅಂದರೆ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಒಟ್ಟಾರೇ "ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳು" ಅಥವಾ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿತರಣೆಯನ್ನು ನಿಯಂತ್ರಿಸುವ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ "ವಸ್ತು ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳು" ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯ "ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ಪತ್ರವ್ಯವಹಾರವಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಹೇಳಿದ್ದರೂ, ಪತ್ರವ್ಯವಹಾರದ ಸ್ವರೂಪದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅವರು ಎಂದಿಗೂ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸಲಿಲ್ಲ, ಇದು ಅವರ ನಡುವಿನ ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಗಳಿಗೆ ಮೂಲವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಭೌತಿಕವಾದವು 1859 ರಲ್ಲಿ, ಅವರ ಜುರ್ ಕೃತಿಕ್ ಡೆರ್ ಪೊಲಿಟಿಸ್ಕನ್ ಒಕೊನೊಮಿಯ ಮುನ್ನುಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಆರ್ಥಿಕತೆ ವಿಮರ್ಶೆಗೆ ಕೊಡುಗೆ ಸಮಾಜದ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆಗೆ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿ ಅವರಿಗೆ ಸೇವೆ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿದ ಊಹೆಯನ್ನು ಸಂಕ್ಷಿಪ್ತವಾಗಿ ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನಂತೆ ರೂಪಿಸಬಹುದು ಎಂದು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಬರೆದರು. ಪುರುಷರು ನಡೆಸುವ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ, ಅವರು ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಅವರ ಇಚ್ಛೆಯಿಂದ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರವಾದ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರವೇಶಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ, ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ವಸ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ಒಂದು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಹಂತಕ್ಕೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಈ ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳ ಒಟ್ಟು ಮೊತ್ತ ಸಮಾಜದ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಚನೆಯನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುತ್ತದೆ, ಇದೇ ನಿಜವಾದ ಅಡಿಪಾಯ, ಅದರ ಮೇಲೆ ಕಾನೂನು ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮೇಲ್ವಿಚಾರಣೆ ಉದ್ಭವಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ರೂಪಗಳಿಗೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಭೌತಿಕ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ವಿಧಾನ ಜೀವನದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಬೌದ್ಧಿಕ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಸ್ವರೂಪವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಅವರ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುವುದು ಪುರುಷರ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯಲ್ಲ; ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ಅವರ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವು ಅವರ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಕಾನೂನಿನ ಮಟ್ಟಕ್ಕೆ ಬೆಳೆದ, ಈ ಊಹೆಯನ್ನು ತರುವಾಯ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಭೌತಿಕ ವಾದ ಎನ್ನಲಾಯಿತು. ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಅದನ್ನು ಅನ್ವಯಿಸಿದರು. ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ತನ್ನ ಕಾರ್ಯಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತವನ್ನು ಹಲವು ವರ್ಷಗಳವರೆಗೆ ಪ್ರತಿಬಿಂಬಿಸಿದರೂ, ಅವನು ಅದನ್ನು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ನಿಖರವಾದ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ರೂಪಿಸಲಿಲ್ಲ; ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಒಂದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ನೈಜತೆಗಳಿಂದಾಗಿ ಅವನಿಗೆ ಸರಿ ಅನ್ನಿಸಿ ದವು. ಅಂದರೆ ಒಬ್ಬರು ಅದರ ಸಾರವನ್ನು ಅಕ್ಷರಶಃ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಂಡರೆ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ವಾಸ್ತವವು ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಚನೆಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ: ಸಮಾಜದ ನಿಜವಾದ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿ ಎಲ್ಲವನ್ನೂ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿರಿಸುವುದು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಚನೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ರಚನೆಯು "ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ವಸ್ತು ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳು", ಅಂದರೆ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಒಟ್ಟಾರೇ "ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳು" ಅಥವಾ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿತರಣೆಯನ್ನು ನಿಯಂತ್ರಿಸುವ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ "ವಸ್ತು ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳು" ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯ "ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ಪತ್ರವ್ಯವಹಾರವಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಹೇಳಿದ್ದರೂ, ಪತ್ರವ್ಯವಹಾರದ ಸ್ವರೂಪದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅವರು ಎಂದಿಗೂ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸಲಿಲ್ಲ, ಇದು ಅವರ ನಡುವಿನ ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಗಳಿಗೆ ಮೂಲವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಚನೆಗೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸಬೇಕು

ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಚನೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಚನೆಗೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸಬೇಕು ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ "ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯ ರೂಪಗಳು" ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುವ ಸೂಪರ್‌ಸ್ಟ್ರಕ್ಚರ್ ಏರುತ್ತದೆ.

ಸೈದ್ಧಾಂತಿಕ ರೂಪಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಚನೆಯ ನಡುವಿನ ಈ ಪತ್ರವ್ಯವಹಾರದ ಸ್ವರೂಪದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಏನನ್ನೂ ಹೇಳುವುದಿಲ್ಲ, ಸೈದ್ಧಾಂತಿಕ ರೂಪಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ರಚನೆಯೊಳಗಿನ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ವಸ್ತು ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಕಾನೂನು, ಆಸ್ತಿಯ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸಿದ ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳ ನಡುವಿನ ಸಂಘರ್ಷದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಜಾಗೃತರಾಗುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಬೇರೆ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇಳುವುದಾದರೆ, "ಪುರುಷರಿಗೆ ಪ್ರವೇಶಿಸಬಹುದಾದ ಉತ್ಪಾದನಾ ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳ ಒಟ್ಟು ಮೊತ್ತವು ಸಮಾಜದ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ" ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಾಜದ ತಳಪಾಯ ದಲ್ಲಿದೆ. "ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ರಚನೆ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳ ಜೀವನ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳಿಂದ ನಿರಂತರವಾಗಿದೆ. ಅವರು ವಾಸ್ತವದಲ್ಲಿರುವಂತೆ, ಅದು ನಟನೆ ಮತ್ತು ಭೌತಿಕವಾಗಿ ಉತ್ಪಾದಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ನಡುವೆ ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳು ಕಾನೂನು ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳಂತೆಯೇ ವಸ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಅವಲಂಬಿತವಾಗಿದೆ. ಆರ್ಥಿಕತೆಯ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕತೆಯ ಈ ಅಡಿಪಾಯ ಪ್ರಾಸಂಗಿಕ ಅಂಶವಲ್ಲ: ಇದು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆಯನ್ನು ಬಣ್ಣಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದು ದಾಸ್ ಕ್ಯಾಪಿಟಲ್ ಮತ್ತು ಡೈಡಾಲ್ಫ್ ಐಡಿಯಾಲಜಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತದೆ. 1844 ರ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ತಾತ್ವಿಕ ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳು ಸಮಾಜದ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಕೆಲಸದ ಕಾಲಕ್ಕೆ ನೇರವಾಗಿ ಹೋಗಲು, ಮಾನವೀಯತೆಗಾಗಿ ಅವರ ಸಮಗ್ರ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮದ ಮೇಲೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಿಸಬೇಕು. **ಕಮ್ಯುನಿಸ್ಟ್ ಮ್ಯಾನಿಫೆಸ್ಟೋ ಮತ್ತು ದಾಸ್ ಕ್ಯಾಪಿಟಲ್** ನಂತರ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಚಿಂತನೆಯನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಇದು ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಮಾನವ ಸ್ವಭಾವದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನ ಮಾನವನ ಅಗತ್ಯದಿಂದ ಆರಂಭವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. "ಮ್ಯಾನ್," ಅವರು 1844 ರ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ತಾತ್ವಿಕ ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಬರೆದಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಮಾನವ ಮೊದಲನೆಯದಾಗಿ ನೈಸರ್ಗಿಕ ಜೀವಿ ಮತ್ತು ಜೀವಂತ ನೈಸರ್ಗಿಕ ಜೀವಿಯಾಗಿ, ಅವನು ಒಂದು ಕಡೆ ನೈಸರ್ಗಿಕ ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳು, ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದಾನೆ. ಈ ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಅವನಲ್ಲಿ ಯೋಗ್ಯತೆಗಳು, ಪ್ರವೃತ್ತಿಗಳಾಗಿ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿವೆ. ಮತ್ತೊಂದೆಡೆ, ವಸ್ತುನಿಷ್ಠ, ನೈಸರ್ಗಿಕ, ದೈಹಿಕ, ಸೂಕ್ಷ್ಮ ಜೀವಿಯಾಗಿ, ಅವನು ಬಳಲುತ್ತಿರುವ, ಅವಲಂಬಿತ ಮತ್ತು ಸೀಮಿತ ಜೀವಿ. ಅಂದರೆ, ಅವನ ಪ್ರವೃತ್ತಿಯ ವಸ್ತುಗಳು ಅವನ ಹೊರಗೆ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿವೆ, ಅವನಿಂದ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ, ಆದರೆ ಅವನ ಅಗತ್ಯದ ವಸ್ತುಗಳು. , ಅವನ ಗಣನೀಯ ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳ ಸಾಕ್ಷಾತ್ಕಾರ ಮತ್ತು ದೃಢೀಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಅವಶ್ಯಕ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಮಾನವ ಇತಿಹಾಸದ ನಿರ್ಗಮನದ ಹಂತವೆಂದರೆ ಜೀವಂತ ಮಾನವರು, ಅವರು ಕೆಲವು ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕ ಅಗತ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಪೂರೈಸಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. "ಮೊದಲ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಸತ್ಯವೆಂದರೆ ಈ ಅಗತ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಪೂರೈಸುವ ಸಾಧನಗಳ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆ." ಈ ತೃಪ್ತಿ, ಪ್ರತಿಯಾಗಿ, ಹೊಸ ಅಗತ್ಯಗಳಿಗೆ ದಾರಿ ತೆರೆಯುತ್ತದೆ. ಮಾನವ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಯು ಮೂಲಭೂತವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯೊಂದಿಗಿನ ಹೋರಾಟವಾಗಿದ್ದು ಅದು ಮಾನವ ಅಗತ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಪೂರೈಸುವ ಸಾಧನವಾಗಿದೆ: ಪಾನೀಯ, ಆಹಾರ, ಬಟ್ಟೆ, ಮಾನವ ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ನಂತರ ಮಾನವ ಬೌದ್ಧಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಕಲಾತ್ಮಕ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯಗಳು. ಈ ಕಾರ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ, ಜನರು ತಮ್ಮ ಮೂಲಕ ತಮ್ಮನ್ನು ತಾವು ಮಾನವೀಕರಿಸುವ ಉತ್ಪಾದಕ ಜೀವಿಗಳಾಗಿ ತಮ್ಮನ್ನು ಕಂಡುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇದಲ್ಲದೆ, ಅವರು ತಮ್ಮನ್ನು ನೈಸರ್ಗಿಕವಾಗಿಸುವಾಗ ಅವರು ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಮಾನವೀಕರಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.

ಸೃಜನಶೀಲ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಯ ಅವಕಾಶವೇ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯ:

ಅವರ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಯಿಂದ, ಅವರ ಶ್ರಮದಿಂದ, ಅವರು ತಮ್ಮ ಗುರುತನ್ನು ಕರಗತ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಸ್ವಭಾವದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಅರಿತುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ, ಅದೇ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಅವರು ಮುಕ್ತ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯಿಂದ ಹುಟ್ಟಿದ ಅವರು ಅದನ್ನು ವಿರೋಧಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ ಮಾನವರಾಗುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಹೋರಾಟದಲ್ಲಿ ತಮ್ಮನ್ನು ಅದರಿಂದ ಬೇರ್ಪಡಿಸುವ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅರಿವು ಮೂಡಿಸುತ್ತದೆ, ಅವರು ತಮ್ಮ ನೆರವೇರಿಕೆಯ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಗಳನ್ನು

ಕಂಡುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ, ಅವರ ನಿಜವಾದ ನಿಲುವಿನ ಸಾಕ್ಷಾತ್ಕಾರ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯ ಉದಯವು ಹೋರಾಟದಿಂದ ಬೇರ್ಪಡಿಸಲಾಗದು. ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ವಾಧೀನಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಮೂಲಕ, ಅವರು ಕಂಡುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ, "ಇತಿಹಾಸ ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯಲ್ಪಡುವ ಎಲ್ಲವೂ ಮಾನವ ಶ್ರಮದ ಮೂಲಕ ಮನುಷ್ಯನನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸುವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆ, ಮನುಷ್ಯನಿಗೆ ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯಾಗುವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯೇ ಹೊರತು ಬೇರೇನೂ ಅಲ್ಲ. ಹೀಗೆ ಮನುಷ್ಯನು ತನ್ನ ಸ್ವಂತ ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಗೆ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾದ ಮತ್ತು ನಿರಾಕರಿಸಲಾಗದ ಪುರಾವೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದಾನೆ. ಅದರ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಆಯಾಮದಲ್ಲಿ ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡರೆ, ಮಾನವ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಯು "ಮನುಷ್ಯನಿಗೆ, ಮನುಷ್ಯನು ಸರ್ವೋಚ್ಚ ಜೀವಿ" ಎಂದು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ದೇವರು, ಸೃಷ್ಟಿ ಮತ್ತು ಆಧ್ಯಾತ್ಮಿಕ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಮಾತನಾಡುವುದು ವ್ಯರ್ಥವಾಗಿದೆ . ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ ಸ್ವಾಭಾವಿಕವಾಗಿ, ಮಾನವರು ತಮಗೇ ಸಾಕಾಗುತ್ತಾರೆ: ಅವರು ಮಾನವೀಯತೆಯ ಪೂರ್ಣತೆಯನ್ನು ಅದರ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಪುನಃ ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಆದಾಗ್ಯೂ, ಬಂಡವಾಳಶಾಹಿ ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸಿಸುವ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯು ನಿಜವಾಗಿಯೂ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರನಲ್ಲ. ಅವರ ಕೀರ್ತಿ ಜೀವಿ; ಅವನ ಜಗತ್ತಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಅವನು ಮನೆಯಲ್ಲಲ್ಲ. ಎಂಬ ಕಲ್ಪನೆ ಪರಕೀಯತೆ, ಇದು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ಹೆಗೆಲ್ನಿಂದ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಲುಡ್ವಿಗ್ ಪ್ಯೂರ್ಬಾಚ್, ತನ್ನ ಯೌವನದ ಬರಹಗಳಿಂದ ಪ್ರಾರಂಭಿಸಿ ದಾಸ್ ಕ್ಯಾಪಿಟಲ್ ಮೂಲಕ ಮುಂದುವರಿಯುವ ತನ್ನ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ಲಿಖಿತ ಕೆಲಸದಲ್ಲಿ ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸುತ್ತಾನೆ . ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ತಾತ್ವಿಕ ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕರ ಪರಕೀಯತೆಯು ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕನು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಎಂಬ ಅಂಶದಿಂದ ಹೊರಹೊಮ್ಮುತ್ತದೆ. ಅವನು ಸೇವಿಸಬೇಕಾದಷ್ಟು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಉತ್ಪಾದಿಸುತ್ತಾನೆ, ಮತ್ತು ಅವನು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಷ್ಟೂ ಅವನು ತನ್ನನ್ನು ತಾನೇ ಅಪಮೌಲ್ಯಗೊಳಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾನೆ, ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಅವನ ಉತ್ಪನ್ನ ಮತ್ತು ಅವನ ಶ್ರಮವು ಅವನಿಂದ ದೂರವಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಕೆಲಸಗಾರನ ಜೀವನವು ಅವನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸಿದ ಆದರೆ ಅವನದಲ್ಲದ ವಸ್ತುಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಅವಲಂಬಿತವಾಗಿದೆ, ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಅವನು ತನ್ನ ದುಡಿಮೆಯ ಮೂಲಕ ತನ್ನ ಸರಿಯಾದ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಕಂಡುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಬದಲು, ಅವನಿಗೆ ಹೊರಗಿನ ವಸ್ತುಗಳ ಈ ಜಗತ್ತಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾನೆ: ಕೆಲಸವಿಲ್ಲ, ವೇತನವಿಲ್ಲ. ಈ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕರು ಕಾಂಕ್ರೀಟ್ ಮಾನವೀಯತೆಯ ಪೂರ್ಣತೆಯನ್ನು ನಿರಾಕರಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. "ಮನುಷ್ಯನ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಜೀವಿ ಪ್ರಕೃತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಅವನ ಬೌದ್ಧಿಕ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯಗಳು, ಅವನಿಗೆ ಅನ್ಯವಾಗಿರುವ ಜೀವಿಯಾಗಿ, ಅವನ ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವದ ಸಾಧನವಾಗಿ ರೂಪಾಂತರಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ." ಪ್ರಕೃತಿ, ಅವನ ದೇಹ ಅವನ ಆಧ್ಯಾತ್ಮಿಕ ಸಾರ ಅವನಿಗೆ ಪರಕೀಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. "ಮನುಷ್ಯನನ್ನು ಮನುಷ್ಯನಿಗೆ ಪರಕೀಯಗೊಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ." ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ಅತ್ಯುನ್ನತ ಹಂತಕ್ಕೆ ಒಯ್ಯುವಾಗ ಖಾಸಗಿ ಆಸ್ತಿಯು "ಅನ್ಯಗೊಳಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟ ದುಡಿಮೆಯ ಉತ್ಪನ್ನವಾಗಿದೆ ಶ್ರಮವು ತನ್ನನ್ನು ತಾನು ದೂರಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಸಾಧನವಾಗಿದೆ ಈ ಪರಕೀಯತೆಯ ಸಾಕ್ಷಾತ್ಕಾರ." ಇದು ಅದೇ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ " ಅನ್ಯಗೊಳಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟ ಮಾನವ ಜೀವನದ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾದ ವಸ್ತು ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ " ಆಗಿದೆ ಎಂದರೆ ತಪ್ಪಾಗಲಾರದು.

ಕಾನೂನು, ನೈತಿಕತೆ, ಆಧ್ಯಾತ್ಮಿಕತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಧರ್ಮಕ್ಕೆ ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದ ಇತಿಹಾಸವಿಲ್ಲ

ಬಂಡವಾಳಶಾಹಿ ಖಾಸಗಿಯಾಗಿ ಸ್ವಾಧೀನಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ. ಮಾರುಕಟ್ಟೆ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯು ವಿಶೇಷತೆ, ತುಂಡು ಕೆಲಸ ಮತ್ತು ದೊಡ್ಡ ಉದ್ಯಮಗಳ ಸ್ಥಾಪನೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕರ ಪರಕೀಯತೆಯನ್ನು ತೀವ್ರಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಹೀಗೆ ಕೆಲಸಗಾರನ ಶ್ರಮಶಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಇತರರ ಜೊತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅವನು ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕವಾಗಿ ಯಾರ ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ಅರಿಯದ ಸಂಯೋಜನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಸಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಹೀಗೆ ಮಾನವ ಉತ್ಪನ್ನಗಳಾಗಿ ತಮ್ಮ ಗುಣಮಟ್ಟವನ್ನು ಕಳೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕರ ಉತ್ಪನ್ನಗಳು ಮಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ವಸ್ತುಗಳಾಗಿವೆ, ಅಂದರೆ ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ಖಾಸಗಿಯಾಗಿ ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಅವುಗಳಿಂದ ವಂಚಿತರಾದ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮನ್ನು ತಾವು

ಸಲ್ಲಿಸುವ ಅನ್ಯಲೋಕದ ಮತ್ತು ದಬ್ಬಾಳಿಕೆಯ ಸತ್ಯಗಳಾಗಿವೆ. ಮಾರುಕಟ್ಟೆ ಆರ್ಥಿಕತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಸ್ತುಗಳ ವಿನಿಮಯವು ಹಣದಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬ ಅಂಶದಿಂದ ವಸ್ತುಗಳಿಗೆ ಈ ಸಲ್ಲಿಕೆಯು ಅಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿದೆ. ಕಾನೂನು, ನೈತಿಕತೆ, ಆಧ್ಯಾತ್ಮಿಕತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಧರ್ಮಕ್ಕೆ ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದ ಇತಿಹಾಸವಿಲ್ಲ. "ತಮ್ಮ ವಸ್ತು ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯನ್ನು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಪಡಿಸುವ ಪುರುಷರು ತಮ್ಮ ನೈಜ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವದೊಂದಿಗೆ ತಮ್ಮ ಆಲೋಚನಾ ವಿಧಾನಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅವರ ಆಲೋಚನಾ ವಿಧಾನಗಳ ಉತ್ಪನ್ನಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾರ್ಪಡಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ." ಬೇರೆ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇಳುವುದಾದರೆ, "ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುವುದು ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯಲ್ಲ. ಇದು ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುವ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವ." ಬಂಡವಾಳಶಾಹಿ ಸಮಾಜವು ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನಾಗರಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ನಟ ಎಂದು ವಿಂಗಡಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ದ್ವಂದ್ವತೆಯು ಅವನ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪರಕೀಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಸುತ್ತದೆ, ಇದು ಬೂರ್ಜ್ವಾಗಳ ಕಾರ್ಯಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಯಿಂದ ಮತ್ತಷ್ಟು ತೀವ್ರಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ. ರಾಜ್ಯ 19ನೇ ಶತಮಾನದ ಆರಂಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮಾಜದ ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದಿಂದ, ಆಸ್ತಿ ವರ್ಗವು ಇತರ ವರ್ಗಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಪ್ರಾಬಲ್ಯ ಸಾಧಿಸುವ ಸಾಧನವಾಗಿ ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ರಾಜ್ಯವನ್ನು ನೋಡಿದರು. ತನ್ನ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆಯ ಉದ್ದಕ್ಕೂ, ಬಂಡವಾಳಶಾಹಿಯ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಯು ಹೆಚ್ಚುತ್ತಿರುವ ವಿರೋಧಾಭಾಸಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ಇರುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ಮಾರ್ಕ್ಸ್ ವಾದಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಉದಾ: ಯಂತ್ರೋಪಕರಣಗಳ ಪರಿಚಯವು ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕ ಬಂಡವಾಳಶಾಹಿಗೆ ಲಾಭದಾಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಅದು ಕಡಿಮೆ ವೆಚ್ಚದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಸರಕುಗಳನ್ನು ಉತ್ಪಾದಿಸಲು ಅನುವು ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುತ್ತದೆ,

ಉಪಸಂಹಾರ:

ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯವೆಂದರೆ ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸಿಸುವ ಎಲ್ಲರಿಗೂ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ, ಸಮಾನತೆ, ಸಹೋದರತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಉತ್ಪನ್ನಗಳ ಸಮಾನ ಹಂಚಿಕೆಯಾದರೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯ ಸಿಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಬಂಡವಾಳಶಾಹಿ ಖಾಸಗಿಯಾಗಿ ಸ್ವಾಧೀನಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ. ಮಾರುಕಟ್ಟೆ ಉತ್ಪಾದನೆಯು ವಿಶೇಷತೆ, ತುಂಡು ಕೆಲಸ ಮತ್ತು ದೊಡ್ಡ ಉದ್ಯಮಗಳ ಸ್ವಾಧೀನವನ್ನು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕರ ಪರಕೀಯತೆಯನ್ನು ತೀವ್ರಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಹೀಗೆ ಕೆಲಸಗಾರನ ಶ್ರಮಶಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಇತರರ ಜೊತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅವನು ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕವಾಗಿ ಯಾರ ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ಅರಿಯದ ಸಂಯೋಜನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಸಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಹೀಗೆ ಮಾನವ ಉತ್ಪನ್ನಗಳಾಗಿ ತಮ್ಮ ಗುಣಮಟ್ಟವನ್ನು ಕಳೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಕಾರ್ಮಿಕರ ಉತ್ಪನ್ನಗಳು ಮಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ವಸ್ತುಗಳಾಗಿವೆ, ಅಂದರೆ ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ಖಾಸಗಿಯಾಗಿ ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಅವುಗಳಿಂದ ವಂಚಿತರಾದ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮನ್ನು ತಾವು ಸಲ್ಲಿಸುವ ಅನ್ಯಲೋಕದ ಮತ್ತು ದಬ್ಬಾಳಿಕೆಯ ಸತ್ಯಗಳಾಗಿವೆ. ಮಾರುಕಟ್ಟೆ ಆರ್ಥಿಕತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಸ್ತುಗಳ ವಿನಿಮಯವು ಹಣದಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬ ಅಂಶದಿಂದ ವಸ್ತುಗಳಿಗೆ ಈ ಸಲ್ಲಿಕೆಯು ಅಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

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 ಹೆಚ್.ಜಿ.ಲಕ್ಷ್ಮಪ್ಪ, ಗೌಡ ೧೯೮೩
 ದಿನಪತ್ರಿಕೆಗಳು, (ಪ್ರಜಾವಾಣಿ, ಕನ್ನಡ ಪ್ರಭ, ಡೆಕ್ಕನ್ ಹೆರಾಲ್ಡ್, ಮತ್ತು ನಿಯತಕಾಲಿಕೆಗಳು)
 ಅಂತರಜಾಲದ ಅನ್ವೇಷಣೆ
 ಸಮಾವೇಶಗಳು, ಕಾರ್ಯಾಗಾರಗಳು, ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳು, ಕರಪತ್ರಗಳು ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ.....

ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಿಳಾ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯತೆ: ಒಂದು ಅಧ್ಯಯನ

ಡಾ.ಪ್ರಭು ಎಸ್.ಬಿ.

ಅತಿಥಿ ಉಪನ್ಯಾಸಕರು

ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ವಿಭಾಗ

ಮಹಾರಾಣಿ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಕಲಾ ಕಾಲೇಜು

ಮೈಸೂರು

ಸಾರಲೇಖ: ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯು ಭಾರತದ ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿದ್ದು 20ನೇ ಶತಮಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಶ್ವದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪರಿವರ್ತನೆಯ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಹುತೇಕ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳು ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರವೆಲ್ಲವೂ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬರಿಗೂ ಸಮಾನವಾಗಿ ಹಂಚಿಕೆಯಾಗಬೇಕಾಗಿರುವುದು ಒಂದು ಮಹತ್ತರ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಮೂಲ ಆಶಯಗಳಾದ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ, ಸಮಾನತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಭ್ರಾತೃತ್ವದ ಅಂಶಗಳು ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ನಾಗರಿಕನಿಗೂ ದೊರಕಿಸಬೇಕಾಗಿರುವುದೇ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯನ್ನು ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾವನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ 4ನೇ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜ್ಯ ನೀತಿ ನಿರ್ದೇಶಕ ತತ್ವಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯನ್ನು ಸೇರಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತಪಡಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳ ಮಹತ್ವ ಮತ್ತು ಅವುಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಇಡೀ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಜಾತಿಯ ಜನಾಂಗದ ಪುರುಷ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಂತೆ ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾಪಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ಭಾರತದ 1952ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ರಚನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸಿದ ಪಂಡಿತ ಜವಾಹರ್‌ಲಾಲ್ ನೆಹರೂರವರು ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಮುನ್ನುಡಿ ಹಾಕಿದರು. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಬಾಬಾ ಸಾಹೇಬ್ ಡಾ.ಬಿ.ಆರ್.ಅಂಬೇಡ್ಕರ್ ರವರು ತಮ್ಮ ನಿರಂತರ ಹೋರಾಟದ ಮೂಲಕ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯವನ್ನು ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಸೇರ್ಪಡೆಗೊಳಿಸಿ ಒದಗಿಸಿದರು. ಈ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಂದಿನ ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಆಳುವ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ತತ್ವವಾದ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ತತ್ವವನ್ನು ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಗೊಳಿಸಿ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠಾಪಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಅವರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲೆಡೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವಾಗುವುದು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಮೂಲ ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿದೆ. 1954ರ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸ್ವಯಂ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳ ಸಚಿವರ ಸಮ್ಮೇಳನದಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಗ್ರಾಮ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ಸಮಿತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸ್ವಯಂ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸಮಿತಿಗಳು ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಕುರಿತು ಚರ್ಚಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಅನೇಕ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸುಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಹೆಜ್ಜೆ ನೀಡುವುದನ್ನು ನೀಡುವಂತೆ ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಪಂಚವಾರ್ಷಿಕ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಆಡಳಿತದ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಯಿಂದ ಜಿಲ್ಲಾ ಮಟ್ಟದ ಆಡಳಿತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತರಲಾಯಿತು. ಮಹಿಳಾ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯತೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಸ್ವಾವಲಂಬಿ ಜೀವನವನ್ನು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಪಡಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಜೀವನವನ್ನು ಸಂಯುಕ್ತಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಸಹಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಈ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದಿಂದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಪುರುಷರಷ್ಟೆ ಸಮಾನವಾದ ಹಕ್ಕು ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ದೊರಕುತ್ತದೆ. 1957 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಸ್ಲೋರಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಆಯುಕ್ತರ ಸಮ್ಮೇಳನವು ಸಮುದಾಯ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಪಂಚಾಯ್ತಿಗಳು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ಪಂಚಾಯ್ತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟವಾದ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಬೇಕೆಂದು ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸು ಮಾಡಲಾಯಿತು. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ತತ್ವ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಲವಂತರಾಯ್ ಮೆಹ್ತಾ ಸಮಿತಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಅಶೋಕ್ ಮೆಹ್ತಾ ಸಮಿತಿಗಳು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಹೆಜ್ಜೆಗಳು. 1979ರ ಅಶೋಕ್ ಮೆಹ್ತಾ ಸಮಿತಿ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸುಗಳು ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಒಳಗೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಮಹತ್ತರವಾದ ಪರಿಣಾಮವನ್ನು ಉಂಟುಮಾಡಿತು. ಈ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತವು ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಗಳಿಸಿ 70 ವರ್ಷಗಳ ಅವಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಆಳುವ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಇಡೀ ಆಡಳಿತವನ್ನು ತಮ್ಮಲ್ಲೇ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಿಸಿಕೊಂಡರೆ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬರ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಕಡಿಮೆಯಾಗುವ ಆತಂಕ ಉಂಟಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ.

ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಅರ್ಥ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತತೆ:-

ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರ □ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರ □ ಜಿಲ್ಲಾ ಆಡಳಿತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ □ ತಾಲ್ಲೂಕು ಆಡಳಿತ ಮತ್ತು ಗ್ರಾಮ ಪಂಚಾಯಿತಿ ಹಂತದವರೆಗೂ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ವಿಸ್ತರಿಸಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಪಂಚದಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ವಿವಿಧತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಏಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸಿರುವ ಹಾಗೂ ಅತೀ ವಿಸ್ತಾರವಾದ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾಗಿ ಭಾರತವು ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧಿ ಪಡೆದಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಜನರಿಂದ ಜನರಿಗಾಗಿ, ಜನರಿಗೋಸ್ಕರ ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ದೇಶದ ಆಡಳಿತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯೂ ವ್ಯಾಪಕವಾಗಿ ವಿಸ್ತಾರಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಭಾರತದ ಸಮಕಾಲೀನ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತ್ಯಕ್ಷ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಪ್ರೇರಿತವಾದ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಅಲೆ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲೆಡೆ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಮೂಲಕ ದಲಿತರ, ಹಿಂದುಳಿದವರ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣವನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸಲು ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯನ್ನು ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಗೊಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರಿಗೆ ಒದಗಿಸುವ ನ್ಯಾಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಾನತೆಯ ಬಲವರ್ಧನೆಗಾಗಿ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳು ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಿ ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲರಾಗಿ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು

ಪಡೆದು ಚಲಾಯಿಸಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳ ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕ, ಕೌಟುಂಬಿಕ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳು ಅನೇಕ ಆತಂಕಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಾಗಿದೆ. ಇವುಗಳಿಂದಾಗಿ ಅವರ ಸಂಘಟನೆ, ಜಾಗೃತಿ, ನಾಯಕತ್ವ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಇನ್ನಿತರ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳು ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂಬ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಗಳು ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ಯೋಗ್ಯವಾದ ವಾತಾವರಣವನ್ನು ಕೆಳ ಹಂತದಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸಿದರೆ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತ ಸ್ಥಾನಗಳ ಪಾಲುದಾರಿಕೆಯ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವು ಗಟ್ಟಿಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಅಧಿಕಾರವೆಲ್ಲವು ಕೇವಲ ಒಂದೇ ಹಂತದಲ್ಲಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತವಾಗುವುದರ ಬದಲಾಗಿ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ ಹಂತಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವಾಗಿರಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವಾಗಿದೆ. ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ರಚನಾಕಾರರ ಮೂಲ ಆಶಯದಂತೆ ಈ ದೇಶದ ಶೋಷಿತರ, ದಲಿತರ, ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ವರ್ಗಗಳ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಗಾಗಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರದ ಹಂಚಿಕೆಯು ಅತ್ಯಗತ್ಯವಾದುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಇತ್ತೀಚಿನ ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಬಲವಂತರು, ಮೇಲ್ವರ್ಗದವರು, ಶ್ರೀಮಂತಶಾಹಿಗಳು ಇಡೀ ದೇಶದ ಅಧಿಕಾರವೆಲ್ಲವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಭಾವದ ಮೂಲಕ, ಹಣದ ಮೂಲಕ ಕೊಂಡುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿದ್ದು ಅಧಿಕಾರವು ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥಿತವಾಗಿ ಅನೇಕರಿಗೆ ಅಂದರೆ ದುರ್ಬಲರಿಗೆ, ಬಲಹೀನರಿಗೆ ಕೈಗೆಟುಕದಿರುವುದು ವಿಪರ್ಯಾಸಕರ ಸಂಗತಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವಾಗಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಪ್ರಬಲರ ದೌರ್ಜನ್ಯ, ದಬ್ಬಾಳಿಕೆ, ಶೋಷಣೆ ಮನೋಭಾವನೆಗಳು ಕಡಿಮೆಯಾಗಬೇಕು. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಅತೀ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ವಂಶಪಾರಂಪರ್ಯ ಆಡಳಿತವು ಕೊನೆಯಾಗಬೇಕೆಂಬುದು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತತೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವು ಆಧುನಿಕ ಭಾರತದ ಸಂಕೀರ್ಣ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಅತೀ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾದ ಅಂಶವಾಗಿದ್ದು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಹೊರಹೊಮ್ಮಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಮೂಲಕ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣವನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸಲು ಮಹಿಳಾ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಯನ್ನು ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಗೊಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ಯೋಗ್ಯವಾದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವಾತಾವರಣವನ್ನು ಕೆಳಹಂತದಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸಿದರೆ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತ ಸ್ಥಾನಿಕ ಪಾಲುದಾರಿಕೆಯ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಗಟ್ಟಿಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳು:-

1. ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಅರ್ಥವನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಯುವುದು.
2. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತತೆಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅರಿಯುವುದು.
3. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಮೂಲ ಆಶಯವಾದ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಿಳಾ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥೈಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು
4. ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಅಧಿನಿಯಮಕ್ಕೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿ ಮಹಿಳಾ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ಥಾನಮಾನಗಳನ್ನು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸುವುದು.
5. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಕಾಲಘಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ತಿಳಿಯುವುದು.

ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆ:-

ಭಾರತದ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿದಾಗ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಜನರು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮಾನವಾದ ಅವಕಾಶಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಬೇಕೆಂಬುದು ಅತ್ಯವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ. ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಜಾರಿಯಾದ ನಂತರದಿಂದ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಾತ್ಮಕ ಅವಕಾಶಗಳು ಹಾಗೂ 1993ರ 73 & 74ನೇ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಗಳು ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಬಲಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಜಾತೀಯ, ಜನಾಂಗದ, ಧರ್ಮದ ಜನರು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಪಾಲ್ಗೊಳ್ಳುವಂತಾಯಿತು. ಅಂದರೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಶಾಸನಬದ್ಧ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಿ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬರಿಗೂ ಸಮಾನವಾದ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಹಂಚಿಕೆ ಮಾಡುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸಿದೆ. ಇಂದು ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ನಿರಂಕುಶ ಧೋರಣೆಯನ್ನು ತಪ್ಪಿಸುವ ಸಲುವಾಗಿ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಹಾಗೂ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರವಾದ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಚಲಾಯಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯತೆಗೆ ಅತಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆ ನೀಡಿದೆ.

ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಬಗೆಗಿನ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ:-

ಬ್ರಿಟೀಷರು ಭಾರತವನ್ನು ಆಳುತ್ತಿದ್ದ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಸ್‌ರಾಯ್ ಆಗಿದ್ದ ಲಾರ್ಡ್‌ರಿಪ್ಪನ್‌ನ ನಂತರ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅಮೂಲಾಗ್ರ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಯನ್ನು ತರಲು ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಯ ಬಗೆಗೆ ಕನಸು ಕಂಡವರು ದಿ.ರಾಜೀವ್‌ಗಾಂಧಿ. ಇವರು ಭಾರತದ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಪ್ರಯೋಗವನ್ನು ಗಂಭೀರವಾಗಿ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡಿ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ದೇಶದಾದ್ಯಂತ ಏಕರೂಪದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಶಕ್ತಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಸದುದ್ದೇಶದಿಂದ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಮಾಡಲು ಕ್ರಮ ಕೈಗೊಂಡರು.

ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ 4ನೇ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ 36 ರಿಂದ 51ನೇ ವಿಧಿಗಳವರೆಗೆ ರಾಜ್ಯ ನೀತಿ ನಿರ್ದೇಶಕ ತತ್ವಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ತಿಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದ್ದು, 40ನೇ ವಿಧಿಯು ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಗ್ರಾಮ ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಗಳನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಿ, ಸ್ವಯಂ ಆಡಳಿತ ಘಟಕಗಳಾಗಿ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ಅಗತ್ಯವಾದ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸಿಕೊಡಬೇಕು ಎಂದು ತಿಳಿಸಿದೆ. ಇದನ್ನು ಪರಿಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ ಸಾಧಿಸಲು ರಾಜೀವ್ ಗಾಂಧಿರವರು ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಮುಂದಾದರು. ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಖಚಿತತೆ, ನಿರಂತರತೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಬಲವನ್ನು ಕೊಡುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ಕೆಲವು ಮೂಲಭೂತವಾದ ಹಾಗೂ ಕಾನೂನಿನ ಅಗತ್ಯವಾದ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒದಗಿಸಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಒಂದು ಹೊಸ ಭಾಗವನ್ನು ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಮೂಲಕ ಸೇರಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯ ಪಟ್ಟರು. ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕ್ರಾಂತಿಕಾರಿ ಬದಲಾವಣೆ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯ ನೀಡುವ ಈ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಲೋಕಸಭೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಪಕ್ಷ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಗೆ ಅಗತ್ಯವಾದಷ್ಟು ಬಹುಮತ ಹೊಂದಿರಲಿಲ್ಲ. ಅಧಿಕಾರ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯ, ಹಿಂದುಳಿದ ವರ್ಗಗಳ ಹಿತ ಚಿಂತಕರೆಲ್ಲರೂ ಒಂದಾಗಿ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸಭೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಯನ್ನು ಒಂದೇ ಒಂದು ಮತದ ಅಂತರದಿಂದ ಸೋಲಿಸಿದ್ದು, ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ದುರಂತ. ಆದರೆ 1989ರಲ್ಲಿ ವಿ.ಪಿ.ಸಿಂಗ್‌ರ ನೇತೃತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್‌ನೇತರ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಕೇಂದ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಬಂದಿತು. ಆಗ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಸಶಕ್ತಗೊಳಿಸಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ವಂಚಿತ ವರ್ಗಕ್ಕೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ನೀಡುವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಈ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಮೌನತಾಳಿದ್ದು ಒಂದು ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಸತ್ಯ. ಕ್ರಾಂತಿಕಾರಕ ಬದಲಾವಣೆ ತರುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಸ್ಥಾನಗಳ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡುವ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಜಾರಿಗೆ ಬರಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಮತ್ತೆ ಕೇಂದ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಅಧಿಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಬರಬೇಕಾಯಿತು. 1991ರಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್‌ನ ಪಿ.ವಿ.ನರಸಿಂಹರಾವ್ ರವರು ಪ್ರಧಾನಿಯಾದ ಮೇಲೆ ರಾಜೀವ್ ಗಾಂಧಿಯವರ ಕನಸುಗಳನ್ನು ಆಶಯಗಳನ್ನು ಪೂರ್ಣಗೊಳಿಸಲು 73 ಮತ್ತು 74ನೇ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಗಳನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಿ ಈ ದೇಶದ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅದ್ಭುತವಾದ ರಕ್ತರಹಿತ ಕ್ರಾಂತಿಗೆ ನಾಂದಿ ಹಾಡಿದರು. ಆ ನಂತರದಲ್ಲಿ ಇಡೀ ಭಾರತದಾದ್ಯಂತ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲೂ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ತತ್ವವು ಭದ್ರವಾಗಿ ನೆಲೆಯೂರಿತು ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

ಹೀಗೆ ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಗಳು ಎಂಬ ಹೆಸರಿನ 73ನೇ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ 243 ರಿಂದ 234ಎ ವಿಧಿಯವರೆಗೆ ಒಳಗೊಂಡು 9ನೇ ಭಾಗವನ್ನು ಹೊಸದಾಗಿ ಸೇರಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಇದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ 11ನೇ ಅನುಸೂಚಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಗಳು ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಬೇಕಾದ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಕರ್ತವ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ 40ನೇ ವಿಧಿಗೆ ರಾಜ್ಯ ನೀತಿ-ನಿರ್ದೇಶಕ ತತ್ವಗಳಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜ್ಯವು ಗ್ರಾಮ ಪಂಚಾಯತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಸಂಘಟಿಸಲು ಕ್ರಮ ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕೆಂದು ನಿರ್ದೇಶಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ 74ನೇ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ 243, ಯಿಂದ 243ಎ ವಿಧಿಯವರೆಗೆ 9 ಎ' ಭಾಗವನ್ನು ಸೇರಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ನಗರ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಕ್ಕೂ ಸಹ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಿಸಲಾಯಿತು.

ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣದ ಸದುಪಯೋಗಗಳು:-

ಭಾರತದಂತಹ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಬೃಹತ್ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರವು ಕೇವಲ ಒಂದೇ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತಗೊಂಡರೆ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಎನಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಈ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರದಿಂದ-ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಹಾಗೂ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಮಟ್ಟದವರೆಗೂ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಹಂಚಿಕೆಯಾದಾಗ ಮಾತ್ರ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಮೌಲ್ಯವನ್ನು ಎತ್ತಿ ಹಿಡಿಯಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಇಡೀ ದೇಶದಾದ್ಯಂತ ವಾಸಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಜಾತಿ, ಜನಾಂಗ, ಧರ್ಮ ಹಾಗೂ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಸೇರಿದಂತೆ ಎಲ್ಲರೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡು ಆ ಮೂಲಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ನೆಲೆಗಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಸೂಕ್ತ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯತೆ ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನವು ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ಭಾರತೀಯರಿಗೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಗುರುತಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆಗೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಟ್ಟಿದೆ. ಅದರಂತೆಯೇ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವು ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಇರಬೇಕೆಂಬುದು ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಉದ್ದೇಶವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವು ಆಧುನಿಕ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಗೊಳ್ಳುವುದರಿಂದ ಆಗುವ ಉಪಯೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ಈ ಕೆಳಕಂಡಂತೆ ತಿಳಿದುಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

- ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಯನ್ನು ಹೋಗಲಾಡಿಸುವುದು.
- ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ಭಾರತೀಯ ಪ್ರಜೆಯೂ ಸಹ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳು, ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ, ಸಮಾನತೆ, ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣತ್ವದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸಮರ್ಪಕವಾಗಿ ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಹಾಯಕ.
- ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಮೂಲ ಆಶಯವನ್ನು ಈಡೇರಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿದೆ.
- ದೇಶದ ಬಹುಸಂಖ್ಯಾತ ಜನರು ಗ್ರಾಮಾಂತರ ಪ್ರದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ವಾಸಿಸುವುದರಿಂದ ಸೂಕ್ತವಾದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಪರಿವರ್ತನೆಯಾಗುವಲ್ಲಿ ಸಹಾಯಕವಾದುದು.

- ಕೆಲವೇ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಸೀಮಿತವಾಗಿದ್ದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಜನರಿಗೆ ವಿಸ್ತಾರವಾಯಿತು.
- ಕೇವಲ ಪುರುಷರಿಗೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಸೀಮಿತವಾಗಿದ್ದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೂ ಅವಕಾಶ ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಿದಂತಾಗಿದೆ.
- ನಿರ್ಧಾರ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯು ಮೇಲಿನ ಹಂತದಿಂದ ಕೆಳ ಹಂತದವರೆಗೂ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕೃತವಾದಂತಾಗಿದೆ.
- ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಳೀಯವಾಗಿಯೇ ಶೀಘ್ರವಾಗಿ ಬಗೆಹರಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಹಾಯವಾಗಿದೆ.
- ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಸೂಕ್ತ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆ, ಜಾಗೃತಿ ಮೂಡಿಸಲು ಸಹಾಯಕ.
- ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯು ದೇಶಾದ್ಯಂತ ಬೆಳೆದು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ.
- ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬರೂ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿದೆ.
- ದೇಶದ ಆದಾಯದ ಮೂಲಗಳು ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರ, ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಆಡಳಿತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹಂಚಿಕೆಯಾಗಿದೆ.
- ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳ ಮೇಲಿನ ಒತ್ತಡ ಕಡಿಮೆಯಾಗಿದೆ.
- ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳ ಸದುಪಯೋಗಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ.
- ಇಡೀ ಭಾರತದಾದ್ಯಂತ 3 ಹಂತದ ಸಂಯುಕ್ತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಜಾರಿಯಾಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಪಥದತ್ತ ಮುನ್ನಡೆಯಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.
- ದೇಶದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಗತಿಗಳು ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಜಾತಿ, ಜನಾಂಗ, ಧರ್ಮ ಮತ್ತು ಲಿಂಗದವರಲ್ಲಿ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಉಪಸಂಹಾರ:-

ಬೃಹತ್ ಸಂವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ನೆಲೆಗಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ಅತ್ಯಗತ್ಯವಾದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ನಾವು ಗಮನಿಸಿದಾಗ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬರಿಗೂ ಸಮಾನವಾಗಿ ಪಡೆಯುವ ಅವಕಾಶವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದು, ಸಂವಿಧಾನಬದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯತೆಯ ಮೂಲಕ ಯಾವುದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ತಾರತಮ್ಯತೆಯಿಲ್ಲದೆ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಂತಾಗಬೇಕು. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಕೇಂದ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಬರುವ ಕೆಲವು ಕೋಮುವಾದಿ, ಜಾತಿವಾದಿ, ವಂಶಪಾರಂಪರ್ಯತೆಯಿಂದ ಕೂಡಿದ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಅಧಿಕಾರವೆಲ್ಲವನ್ನು ತಮ್ಮ ಸ್ವಾರ್ಥಹಿತ ಸಾಧನೆಗಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಂಶವನ್ನೇ ಮೂಲ ಆಧಾರವನ್ನಾಗಿ ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣವಾದಾಗ ಮಾತ್ರ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಶೀಲ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾಗಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಅದರಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇಡೀ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯಾಪಕವಾಗಿರುವ ಕೆಲವು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ವಿಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಣ ಮಾಡಬೇಕೆಂಬುದು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೆ ಸಮಾನ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯತೆ ನೀಡುವ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ಪುರುಷರಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಬರಬೇಕು ಆ ಮೂಲಕ ಆಳುವ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಸೂಕ್ತ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಗಳನ್ನು ತರಬೇಕು ಎಂಬುದು ಸಂಶೋಧಕರ ಆಶಯವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಆಧಾರ ಗ್ರಂಥಗಳು:

- ಅ್ಯಡ್ವಾಟೆಡು ಸಿ.ಕೆ.ಬಿ ಚೆಟಿಜಿ ಗಿ.ಸಿ.ಅ್ಯಬೆಟ್ಟಿಜಿ - 1989 - ಹೆಟಿಭಿಚಿಥಿಚಿಚಿ ಖಚಿರಿ ಚೆಟಿಜಿ ಖಿಣಿಚಿಟಿ ಆಜ್ಞಾಪುಡಿಚಿಚಿಚಿ, ಅಡ್ವಾಟೆ ಫಿಚಿಚಿಚಿಚಿ, ಓಜಿ ಆಜ್ಞಾಪುಡಿ
ಡಾ.ದುರ್ಗಾದಾಸ್‌ಬಸು, ಭಾರತದ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಪರಿಚಯ 2ನೇ ಆವೃತ್ತಿ, ಜಿ.ಬಿ.ಪಟ್ನಾಯಕ್ ಮತ್ತು ಯಸೋಬಂತರ್ ಬಸು ಕನ್ನಡಕ್ಕೆ ತರ್ಜುಮೆ - 2015 - ಐಜಿಫಿ ಓಜಿಫಿ - ಪ್ರಕಾಶನದ. ಹರಿಯಾಣ-ಭಾರತ.
ಪ್ರೊ.ಹೆಚ್.ಎಂ.ರಾಜಶೇಖರ್ - ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ, 16ನೇ ಆವೃತ್ತಿ 2017, ಪ್ರಭೋಧ ಪಬ್ಲಿಕೇಷನ್, ಮೈಸೂರು.
ರಾಫ್‌ವೇಂದ್ರ - ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ಅಧಿನಿಯಮ - 1993, ಶ್ರೀ ರಾಫ್‌ವೇಂದ್ರ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ, ಚಿಕ್ಕಪೇಟೆ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು.
ಡಾ. ಗಾಯತ್ರಿ ಎನ್. "ಮಹಿಳಾ ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಲಿಂಗರಾಜಕಾರಣ" ಪ್ರಕಟಣೆ ಲಡಾಯಿ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ -ಗದಗ-2012
ವನಜ "ಹೆಣ್ಣು ಹಕ್ಕು ಹೋರಾಟ" ಪ್ರಕಟಣೆ ಸಮತಾ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಮೈಸೂರು-2003
ಹರೀಶ್ ಆರ್. ಬಸವರಾಜ್, ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಂಚಾಯತ್ ರಾಜ್ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ, 2005 ದೂರ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ, ನಿರ್ದೇಶನಾಲಯ, ಜ್ಞಾನ ಸಹ್ಯಾದ್ರಿ, ಶಂಕರಘಟ್ಟ ಶಿವಮೊಗ್ಗ.
ಸುರೇಶ್ ಕೆ.ಎಂ. ಸ್ವರ್ಧಾ ವಿಜೇತ, ಪಿ.ಡಿ.ಓ. ಮತ್ತು ಗ್ರೇಡ್ - 1, ನೇಮಕಾತಿ ಪರೀಕ್ಷಾ ಮಾರ್ಗದರ್ಶಿ 2016.

ಒಂದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ-ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆ : ಸವಾಲುಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಹಾರಗಳು

ಡಾ. ಮಲ್ಲೇಶ ದೊಡ್ಡಲಕ್ಕಣ್ಣವರ

ಸಹಾಯಕ ಉಪನ್ಯಾಸಕರು, ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ವಿಭಾಗ

ಸಂಗೊಳ್ಳಿ ರಾಯಣ್ಣ ಪ್ರಥಮ ದರ್ಜೆ ಘಟಕ ಪದವಿ ಮಹಾವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ ಬೆಳಗಾವಿ

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ಪೀಠಿಕೆ

ಭಾರತವು ಜಗತ್ತಿನ ಅತಿದೊಡ್ಡ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾಗಿದೆ. ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಭಾರತದ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವು ಸುಮಾರು 96.88 ಕೋಟಿ ಮತದಾರರನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಸಂಸದೀಯ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ದಾಪುಗಾಲು ಹಾಕುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಭಾರತದ ಸಂವಿಧಾನವು ಸಂಯುಕ್ತ ಪದ್ಧತಿಗನುಗುಣವಾಗಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಿದೆ. ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು ಸಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಯಾಗಿದ್ದು, ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಪತಿ, ಉಪರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಪತಿ, ಸಂಸತ್ತಿನ ಉಭಯ ಸದನಗಳಾದ ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜ್ಯಸಭೆ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗದ ಸದನಗಳಾದ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆ ಹಾಗೂ ವಿಧಾನ ಪರಿಷತ್ತಿನ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸಂಘಟಿಸುವ ಅತಿ ಮಹತ್ತರ ಹಾಗೂ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯುತ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿಯವರೆಗೆ 18 ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಯಶಸ್ವಿಯಾಗಿ ನಡೆಸಿಕೊಟ್ಟಿದೆ. ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಆಯೋಗ ಇಲ್ಲಿಯವರೆಗೆ ಅನೇಕ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಮೈಗೂಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದೆ. 'ಒಂದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ, ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆ' ಎಂಬ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ ಇತ್ತೀಚಿನ ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅತೀ ಚರ್ಚಿತ ವಿಷಯವಾಗಿ ಹೊರಹೊಮ್ಮಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಲೇಖನವು 'ಒಂದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ - ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆ' ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಮೇಲೆ ಬೀರಬಹುದಾದ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಹಾಗೂ ಎದುರಾಗಬಹುದಾದ ಸವಾಲುಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸಮರ್ಪಕವಾಗಿ ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸಿದೆ.

ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳು

1. ಒಂದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ-ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥೈಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು.
2. ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದ ಮೇಲೆ ಒಂದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ-ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಪ್ರಭಾವವನ್ನು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸುವುದು
3. ಒಂದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ-ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಸವಾಲುಗಳ ಪರಿಹಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಹುಡುಕುವುದು.
4. ಭಾರತದ ಒಕ್ಕೂಟ ಪದ್ಧತಿ ಮೇಲೆ ಒಂದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ-ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಪ್ರಭಾವವನ್ನು ಮೌಲ್ಯೀಕರಿಸುವುದು.

ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆ

ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಜನರು ತಮ್ಮ ಸಾರ್ವಭೌಮತ್ವವನ್ನು ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸಲು, ಉತ್ತರದಾಯಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಮತ್ತು ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯ ಆಡಳಿತವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸಲು ನಿರ್ಣಾಯಕ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸಿದೆ. ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಆಧಾರಸ್ತಂಭಗಳಾಗಿವೆ. ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಆಡಳಿತ ಹಾಗೂ ನೀತಿ ನಿರೂಪಣೆ ಮೇಲೆ ಪರಿಣಾಮವನ್ನು ಬೀರುತ್ತವೆ. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಸತ್ತಿಗೆ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜ್ಯ ವಿಧಾನ ಸಭೆಗೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯನ್ನು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು ಹೊತ್ತಿಕೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಭಿತವಾಗಿ, ಪಾರದಾರ್ಶಕವಾಗಿ ನಡೆಸುವುದು ಅತಿ ದೊಡ್ಡ ಸವಾಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಅಲ್ಲದೇ ಮೇಲಿಂದ ಮೇಲೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವುದು ವೆಚ್ಚದಾಯಕವೂ ಆಗಿವೆ. ಈ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಹಾಗೂ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆಗಳ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಸುವ "ಒಂದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ-ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆ" ಎಂಬ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ ಇತ್ತೀಚಿನ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜ್ಯ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಅತೀ ಚರ್ಚಿತ ವಿಷಯವಾಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಅದರ ಸವಾಲುಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಒಂದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ-ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ:

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಇತ್ತೀಚಿನ ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನಡೆಸಬೇಕೆಂಬ ಆಡಳಿತ ಪಕ್ಷ ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾವ ಇಟ್ಟಿದೆ. ಈ ಕುರಿತು ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ಚರ್ಚೆಗೆ ಗ್ರಾಸವಾಗಿದೆ. ಒಂದು ದೇಶ- ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಎಂಬ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯು ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಹಾಗೂ ವಿಧಾನ ಸಭೆಗಳ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾದರೆ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಐದು ವರ್ಷಗಳಿಗೊಮ್ಮೆ ನಡೆಸಲು ಸಲಹೆ ನೀಡುವುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಯು ಅಪಾರ ಪ್ರಮಾಣದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ವೆಚ್ಚವನ್ನು ಉಳಿತಾಯಗೊಳಿಸಲು ತನ್ಮೂಲಕ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸುಧಾರಣೆ ತರಬಹುದು ಎಂದು ಇದರ ಸಮರ್ಥಕರು ವಾದಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನಡೆಸುವ ಪದ್ಧತಿ ಪ್ರಪಂಚದ ವಿವಿಧ ಭಾಗಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾರಿಯಲ್ಲಿದೆ. ಬ್ರೆಜಿಲ್, ಫಿಲಿಪೈನ್ಸ್, ಕೊಲಂಬಿಯಾ ಮುಂತಾದ ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧ್ಯಕ್ಷೀಯ ಹಾಗೂ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗದ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಸುವ ಪದ್ಧತಿ ಜಾರಿಯಲ್ಲಿದೆ. ಮತ್ತೊಂದೆಡೆ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಆಫ್ರಿಕಾ ಹಾಗೂ ಸ್ವಿಡನ್‌ನಂತಹ ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗಗಳ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಸಲಾಗಿತ್ತದೆ. ಭಾರತ ಹಾಗೂ ಅಮೇರಿಕಾ ನಂತರದ ಜಗತ್ತಿನ ಮೂರನೇಯ ಅತಿದೊಡ್ಡ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾದ

ಇಂಡೋನೇಷ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಇತ್ತಿಚೆಗೆ ಮೊದಲಬಾರಿಗೆ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸಂಘಟಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಈ ಎಲ್ಲ ಜಗತ್ತಿನ ಅನುಭವಗಳು ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲೂ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಸುವ ಚುನಾವಣೆ 'ಒಂದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ -ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆ' ಗೆ ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಪ್ರಪಂಚದ ಅತಿದೊಡ್ಡ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾದ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯ ಪ್ರಯೋಗ ಅತೀ ಸವಾಲೇನಿಸಿದರೂ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಇಂತಹ ಪ್ರಯೋಗಗಳಿಗೆ ಮುನ್ನುಡಿಯಾಗಬೇಕು.

ಒಂದು ದೇಶ-ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಗಳು

- ಒಂದು ದೇಶ-ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗದ, ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಹೊರೆಯನ್ನು ತಗ್ಗಿಸಬಹುದು.
- ಮೇಲಿಂದ ಮೇಲೆ ಹೇರಲಾಗುವ ನೀತಿ ಸಂಹಿತೆಯಿಂದಾಗಿ ಹಿಂದುಳಿಯುವ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಹಿನ್ನಡೆಯನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆಗೊಳಿಸಬಹುದು.
- "ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಭ್ರಮೆ"ಯಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಆಡಳಿತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊರತಂದು, ನೀತಿಗಳ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನ, ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳ ಜಾರಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಗಮನ ಹರಿಸಬಹುದು.
- ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ ಯಂತ್ರವನ್ನು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯದಿಂದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ತೊಡಗಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಸಹಾಯಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿದೆ.
- ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿನ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸಂದರ್ಭದ ಹಣದ ಹೊಳೆಯನ್ನು ತಗ್ಗಿಸಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.
- ಕಾನೂನು ಆಯೋಗದ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸು ಅನ್ವಯ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿನ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯು ಮತದಾನದ ಹೆಚ್ಚಳದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಹಾಯಕಾರಿಯಾಗಬಹುದು.
- ರಾಜ್ಯ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ವೆಚ್ಚ-ಪರಿಣಾಮಕತ್ವ ಮತ್ತು ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ ದಕ್ಷತೆಯಿಂದ ಉತ್ತಮ ಆಡಳಿತ ಮತ್ತು ನೀತಿ ನಿರಂತರತೆ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುವುದು.

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಹೆಜ್ಜೆಗಳು

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವ ಈ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ ಹೊಸದೇನಲ್ಲ. 1951-52, 1957, 1962 ಹಾಗೂ 1967 ರ ಸಂಸತ್ತು ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜ್ಯ ವಿಧಾನ ಸಭೆಗಳ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಯಿತು. ಕೇರಳ ಹಾಗೂ ಒಡಿಸ್ಸಾ ಮಧ್ಯಂತರ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಿಂದಾಗಿ ಈ ಚಕ್ರವು ಸ್ಥಗಿತಗೊಂಡಿತು. ಆದರೆ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆ ಸುಗಮಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಪರಿಹಾರವಾಗಿ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯನ್ನು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗ 1983ರಲ್ಲಿ ಮೊದಲು ಸೂಚಿಸಿತು. ನ್ಯಾಯಮೂರ್ತಿ ಬಿ.ಪಿ ಜೇವನರೆಡ್ಡಿ ನೇತೃತ್ವದ ಭಾರತದ ಕಾನೂನು ಆಯೋಗವು ತನ್ನ 170 ನೇ ವರದಿಯಲ್ಲಿ "ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳ ಸುಧಾರಣೆ(1999)" ಸಹ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನಡೆಸಲು ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸು ಮಾಡಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಕಾರಣಾಂತರಗಳಿಂದ ಈ ಕಲ್ಪನೆಯು ಫಲಪ್ರಥವಾಗಲಿಲ್ಲ. 2014ರ ನಂತರ ಎನ್.ಡಿ.ಎ. ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಮತ್ತೊಮ್ಮೆ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನಡೆಸುವ "ಒಂದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ-ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆ" ಎಂಬ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ ಹುಟ್ಟುಹಾಕಿತು. 2015 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಸಿಬ್ಬಂದಿ, ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಕುಂದುಕೊರತೆಗಳು, ಕಾನೂನು ನ್ಯಾಯದ ಸಂಸದೀಯ ಸಮಿತಿಯು ತನ್ನ 79 ನೇ ವರದಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ದೀರ್ಘಕಾಲಿನ ಉತ್ತಮ ಆಡಳಿತಕ್ಕೆ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸಲು ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸು ಮಾಡಿತು.

2023 ಸೆಪ್ಟೆಂಬರ್ 2 ರಂದು ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ಪರಿಕ್ಷೀಸಲು ಮಾಜಿ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಪತಿಗಳಾದ ರಾಮನಾಥ್ ಕೋವಿಂದ್ ಅವರ ಅಧ್ಯಕ್ಷತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದು ಉನ್ನತಾಧಿಕಾರ ಸಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ನೇಮಕ ಮಾಡಲಾಯಿತು. ಈ ಸಮಿತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಗೃಹ ಸಚಿವರಾದ ಅಮಿತ ಶಾ, ರಾಜ್ಯಸಭೆಯ ಮಾಜಿ ಪ್ರತಿಪಕ್ಷ ನಾಯಕ ಗುಲಾಂ ನಬಿ ಆಜಾದ್, 15 ನೇ ಹಣಕಾಸು ಆಯೋಗದ ಅಧ್ಯಕ್ಷರಾದ ಎನ್. ಕೆ. ಸಿಂಗ್, ಲೋಕಸಭೆಯ ಮಾಜಿ ಕಾರ್ಯದರ್ಶಿ ಡಾ. ಸುಭಾಷ ಕಶ್ಯಪ್, ಹಿರಿಯ ವಕೀಲರಾದ ಹರೀಶ್ ಸಾಳ್ವೆ, ಮಾಜಿ ಮುಖ್ಯ ವಿಚಕ್ಷಣಾ ಆಯುಕ್ತ ಸಂಜಯ ಕೊಲಾರಿಯವರನ್ನು ಸದಸ್ಯರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸಚಿವ ಅರ್ಜುನ್ ರಾಮ್ ಮೇಘವಾಲ್ ಅವರನ್ನು ವಿಶೇಷ ಆಹ್ವಾನಿತರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಭಾರತದ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಕಾರ್ಯದರ್ಶಿ ಡಾ. ನಿತೇನ್ ಚಂದ್ರ ಅವರನ್ನು ಸದಸ್ಯ ಕಾರ್ಯದರ್ಶಿಯನ್ನಾಗಿ ನೇಮಕ ಮಾಡಲಾಯಿತು.

ಈ ಸಮಿತಿಯು ಸುಮಾರು 191 ದಿನಗಳ ಕಾಲ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆ ಮಾಡಿ ಮಾಡಿ ಇತರೇ ದೇಶಗಳ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿಟ್ಟುಕೊಂಡು ಸುಮಾರು 47 ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳನ್ನು ಸಂದರ್ಶಿಸಿದೆ. ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ 32 ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಏಕಕಾಲದ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯನ್ನು ಸಮರ್ಥಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅಲ್ಲದೇ, ಸಮಿತಿಯು ಅರ್ಥಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಜ್ಞರು ಹಾಗೂ ಭಾರತದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸಮಾಲೋಚನೆ ಮಾಡಿ 18,626 ಪುಟಗಳ ವರದಿಯನ್ನು ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿತು. ಒಂದು ದೇಶ ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಕುರಿತು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರಿಂದ ಸುಮಾರು 21,558 ಸಲಹೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲಾಯಿತು. ಇದರಲ್ಲಿ ಶೇ. 80 ರಷ್ಟು ಜನ ಅದರ ಪರವಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂದು ತಿಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ವರದಿಯನ್ನು ನರೇಂದ್ರ ಮೋದಿ ನ ನೇತೃತ್ವದ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸಚಿವ ಸಂಪುಟ ಅನುಮೋದನೆ ನೀಡಿದೆ.

ರಾಮನಾಥ್ ಕೋವಿಂದ ನೇತೃತ್ವದ ಸಮಿತಿಯು ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನಡೆಸಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಕೆಲವು ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸುಗಳನ್ನು ತನ್ನ ವರದಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟ ಪಡಿಸಿದೆ. ಸಮಿತಿಯು ಭಾರತದ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಕ್ಕೆ ಸುಮಾರು 18 ತಿದ್ದುಪಡೆಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಬೇಕೆಂದು ಸಲಹೆ ನೀಡಿತು.

- ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸನ ಸಭೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನಡೆಸುವ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡೆ ಮಸೂದೆಗೆ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಶಾಸನ ಸಭೆಗಳ ಅನುಮೋದನೆ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆ ಇಲ್ಲ. ಕೇವಲ ಸಂಸತ್ತು ಅಂಗೀಕರಿಸಿದರೆ ಸಾಕು. ಆದರೆ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಗಣಿಸಿದರೆ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಶಾಸನ ಸಭೆಗಳ ಅನುಮೋದನೆ ಅಗತ್ಯ ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳ ವಿಷಯ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಪಟ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿದೆ.
- ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ 82ಎ ವಿಧಿಯ ಸೆರ್ಪಡೆ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಏಕಕಾಲೀನ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತರಲು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಪತಿಗಳು “ನೇಮಕದ ದಿನಾಂಕವನ್ನು ಸೂಚಿಸಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ 83 ಹಾಗೂ 172ರ ವಿಧಿಗಳಿಗೆ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡೆ ತಂದು ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಹಾಗೂ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆಗಳ ಐದು ವರ್ಷಗಳ ಅಧಿಕಾರವಧಿಯನ್ನು “ಪೂರ್ಣ ಅವಧಿ” ಎಂದು ಮರು ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಿಸಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಹಾಗೂ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆ ಅವಧಿಗೆ ಮುನ್ನ ವಿಸರ್ಜಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟರೆ ಹೊಸ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆಯು “ಅವಧಿ ಮೀರಿದ ಅವಧಿಗೆ” ಮಾತ್ರ ಕಾರ್ಯ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜ್ಯ ವಿಧಾನ ಸಭೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸಮ್ಮಿಲನ ಆಗಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಖಚಿತಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಸಂಸತ್ತಿಗೆ ಕಾನೂನು ಮಾಡಲು ಅಧಿಕಾರ ನೀಡುವ ಸಂಬಂಧ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ 324ಎ ವಿಧಿಗೆ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡೆ ತರಬೇಕಾಗುವುದು.
- 325 (2) ವಿಧಿಯು ಎಲ್ಲ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಒಂದೇ ಮತದಾರ ಪಟ್ಟಿ ಸಿದ್ಧಪಡಿಸಲು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗಕ್ಕೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ನೀಡುವುದು.
- ಮೊದಲ ಬಾರಿಗೆ ಎರಡು ಹಂತದಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಬೇಕು ಮೊದಲ ಹಂತದಲ್ಲಿ ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಸುವುದು. ಎರಡನೇಯ ಹಂತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯು 100 ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವುದು.

ಸವಾಲುಗಳು

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನಡೆಸುವುದು ಅಷ್ಟು ಸುಲಭದ ಕಾರ್ಯಸಾಧ್ಯವಲ್ಲ. ಅದನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಅನೇಕ ಸವಾಲು ಹಾಗೂ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ 6456 ಜಾತಿಗಳು 16 ಮತಧರ್ಮಗಳು ಹಾಗೂ 152 ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟುಗಳಿರುವ ಬೃಹತ್ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾಗಿದೆ. ಒಂದು ದೇಶ ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಸುಮಾರು 15,68,000 ಹಳ್ಳಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಯುವ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಹಬ್ಬವಾಗಿದೆ. ಸುಮಾರು 740 ಜಿಲ್ಲೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ 543 ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಸ್ಥಾನಗಳಿಗೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ವಿಧಾನ ಸಭೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಸುವುದು ಸವಾಲೇ ಸರಿ.

- ಪದೆ ಪದೆ ನಡೆಯುವ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಿಂದಾಗಿ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆ ಅಧಿಕವಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಆದರೆ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿನ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಜನಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರಂಕುಶ ಧೊರಣೆ ಬೆಳೆಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಸಹಾಯಕಾರಿಯಾಗಬಹುದು.
- ಸಂಯುಕ್ತ ಪದ್ಧತಿಗೆ ದಕ್ಕೆಯಾಗಬಹುದು ಹಾಗೂ ಅದನ್ನು ದುರ್ಬಲಗೊಳಿಸಬಹುದು.
- ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿನ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಿಸುವುದರಿಂದ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಕಾಳಜಿಗಳನ್ನು ಮರೆಮಾಡಬಹುದು.
- ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಭವಿಷ್ಯವನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆಗೊಳಿಸಬಹುದು.
- ಮತದಾರರು ತಮ್ಮ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಇಚ್ಛೆಯನ್ನು ನಿಯಮಿತವಾಗಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸುವ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಬಂಧಿಸಬಹುದು.
- ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಒಂದೇ ಪಕ್ಷದ ಪರವಾಗಿ ಮತ ಚಲಾಯಿಸಲು ಮತದಾರರ ಮೇಲೆ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರಬಹುದು.
- ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಇಡೀ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನಡೆಸುವುದು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗ ಹಾಗೂ ಭದ್ರತಾ ಪಡೆಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಅಪಾರ ಒತ್ತಡವನ್ನು ಉಂಟು ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಹೆಚ್ಚುವರಿ ಇವಿಎಂ ಹಾಗೂ ವಿ.ವಿ. ಪ್ಯಾಟ್ ಸಂಗ್ರಹಿಸುವುದು, ನಿಯೋಜಿಸುವುದು ಸಮಯ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ದುಬಾರಿಯಾಗಬಹುದು.
- ಅಸ್ಥಿರ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳನ್ನು ನಿಭಾಯಿಸುವುದು ಕಠಿಣವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಪರಿಹಾರಗಳು:

ಯಾವುದೇ ಒಂದು ಹೊಸ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಜಾರಿಗೆ ಹತ್ತು ಹಲವು ಸವಾಲುಗಳು ಹಾಗೂ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳು ಎದುರಾಗುವುದು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಒಂದು-ದೇಶ, ಒಂದು-ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಸಹ ಹೊರತಾಗಿಲ್ಲ. ಆದಾಗ್ಯೂ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಇಂತಹ ಮಹತ್ತರ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನವನ್ನು ತರಾತುರಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾರಿ ತರಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸದೇ ಅದರ ಆಗುಹೋಗುಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸುದೀರ್ಘವಾಗಿ ಚರ್ಚಿಸಿ ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸುವುದು ಉತ್ತಮವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ “ಒಂದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ, ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆ” ಎಂಬ ಮಹತ್ತರ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಹಾಗೂ ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸಲು ಕೆಲವು ಸಲಹೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ.

- ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಇಂತಹ ಮಹತ್ತರ ಯೋಜನೆಯನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಎಲ್ಲ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಬೆಂಬಲ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಉತ್ತಮ.
- ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಎಲ್ಲ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಸುವ ಬದಲು ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕವಾಗಿ ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಕೆಲವು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕವಾಗಿ ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಿ, ನಂತರ ಅದರ ಆಗುಹೋಗುಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡಿ ಇಡೀ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದ್ಯಂತ ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸುವುದು ಉತ್ತಮ.
- ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಈ ಯೋಜನೆಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಮತದಾರರಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾಗೃತಿಗೊಳಿಸಬೇಕು.
- ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿನ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಇರುವ ಆತಂಕಗಳನ್ನು ದೂರವಾಗಿಸಲು ಸಾವಜನಿಕ ಸಂವಾದ, ಜನಜಾಗೃತಿ ಮುಂತಾದ ಚಿಂತನ-ಮಂಥನದ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆ ಇದೆ.

ಕೊನೆಯ ಮಾತು:

ಒಂದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ-ಒಂದು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯು ವೆಚ್ಚ ಉಳಿತಾಯ, ಆಡಳಿತ ನಿರಂತರತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ ದಕ್ಷಣೆ ಸೇರಿದಂತೆ ಹಲವಾರು ಸಂಭಾವ್ಯ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದಾಗ್ಯೂ, ಈ ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾವನೆಯು ಸಂಯುಕ್ತ ಪದ್ಧತಿ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥಾಪನೆಯ ಕಾರ್ಯಸಾಧ್ಯತೆಯ ವಿಷಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಪರಿವರ್ತಕ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಮುಂದುವರೆಯುವ ಮೊದಲಯ ಉತ್ತಮ ರಚನಾತ್ಮಕ ಮತ್ತು ಅಂತರ್ಗತ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಸಂವಾದವು ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತಂದರೆ, ಭಾರತವು ಬೆಲ್ಜಿಯಂ, ಸ್ವೀಡನ್ ಹಾಗೂ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಆಫ್ರಿಕಾದಂತಹ ದೇಶಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾಗತಿಕ ಮಾದರಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದುತ್ತದೆ.

ಗ್ರಂಥಸೂಚಿ

ಭಾರತದ ಕಾನೂನು ಆಯೋಗದ ವರದಿ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ-255, ಮಾರ್ಚ್, 2015

ಭಾರತದ ಕಾನೂನು ಆಯೋಗದ ವರದಿ-2018

ಏಕ್ವಿ ಬಸೋಯಾ, “ಒನ್ ನೇಷನ್-ಒನ್ ಎಲೆಕ್ಷನ್ ಎನಾಲ್ಟೆಸಿಂಗ್ ದಿ ಇಂಪ್ಯಾಕ್ಟ್ ಆನ್ ಇಂಡಿಯನ್ ಪಾಲಿಟಿ” 2023

ರಾಜ್ಯ ಸಭೆಯ 79 ನೇ ವರದಿ 2015

ಅರ್ನಾಲ್ ಚೇಟಿಯಾ “ಒನ್ ನೇಷನ್-ಒನ್ ಎಲೆಕ್ಷನ್: ವಾಟ್ ಇಟ್ ಕುಡ್ ಮೀನ್ ಫಾರ್ ಇಂಡಿಯಾ” ಸೋಷಿಯಲ್ ಆಂಡ್ ರಿಸರ್ಚ್ ಫೌಂಡೇಷನ್- 2020

ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣತ್ವದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ

ನಿಖಿಲ್ ಯು ಎಸ್¹⁰

ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಮಾಜದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ವಿವರಣೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಿರುವ ಬಹುತೇಕ ಚಿಂತಕರವಾದವನ್ನೇಂದರೆ ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಮಾಜವು ಅಸಮಾನತೆಯಿಂದ ಕೂಡಿದೆ. ಈ ಅಸಮಾನತೆ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಕಾರಣವೆಂದರೆ ಅನಿಷ್ಟ ಆಚರಣೆಗಳಾದ ಮೇಲು ಕೀಳು ಅಸ್ವಶ್ಯತೆ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ ಆಚರಣೆಗಳಿವೆ. ಈ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಅನಿಷ್ಟ ಆಚರಣೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಕಾರಣವೆಂದರೆ ಹಿಂದುಯಿಸಂನಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಜಾತಿ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಅದರ ಲಕ್ಷಣವಾಗಿರುವ ಅಸ್ವಶ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಪೋಷಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಬಂದಿರುವ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ಪುರೋಹಿತಶಾಯಿ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ. ಇವರ ಅನಿಷ್ಟ ಆಚರಣೆಗಳು ಯಜ್ಞಯಾಗದಿಗಳ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಬಂಡಾಯವೆದ್ದು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತವು ಉಗಮವಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಎಂಬುದು ಅಂಬೇಡ್ಕರ್ ಹಾದಿಯಾಗಿ ಅಂಬೇಡ್ಕರ್‌ರವರ ವಾದವನ್ನು ಬೆಂಬಲಿಸುವ ಚಿಂತಕರವಾದವೂ ಕೂಡ ಇದೇ ಆಗಿದೆ. ಒಂದು ವೇಳೆ ಈ ಹೇಳಿಕೆಗಳು ನಿಜವೇ ಆಗಿದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥದ ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯ ಆಚರಣೆಗಳ ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಿನ್ನವಾದ ಆಚರಣೆಗಳು ಇರಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಬೌದ್ಧಿಕ ವಲಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಬೌದ್ಧ ಹಾಗೂ ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥಗಳಿಗೂ ಸಾಮ್ಯತೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬಹುದು ಎಂಬುವುದು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಚಿಂತಕರುಗಳ ವಾದ. ಈ ಎರಡು ಪರ ಹಾಗೂ ವಿರೋಧವಾದಗಳ ಸತ್ಯ ಅಸತ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಈ ಲೇಖನದಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಲಾಗುವುದು.

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕಾಲದಿಂದಲೂ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ಪುರೋಹಿತಶಾಯಿಯು ದೇವರ ಹೆಸರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಮೂಡಾಚರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅನ್ವೇಷಿಸಿ ಶೋಷಣೆ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ. ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಅನಿಷ್ಟಗಳನ್ನು ಹುಟ್ಟುಹಾಕಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರು ವೇದ ವಿದ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ಊಳಿದವರಿಗೆ ನೀಡದಂತೆ ವಂಚಿಸಿದವರು ತಮಗೆ ಅನುಕೂಲಕರವಾದ ನಿಯಮಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿ. ಅನಿಷ್ಟ ಆಚರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಚಲಿಸಿ ತರುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ಪುರೋಹಿತಶಾಯಿಯ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಗಟ್ಟಿಗೊಳಿಸಿದರು. ಇದರ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಬಂಡಾಯವೆಂದು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತ ಉದಯವಾಯಿತು ಎಂಬುದು ಅಧುನಿಕ ಚಿಂತಕರವಾದ. ಈ ವಾದಕ್ಕೆ ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾಗಿ 'ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ಮೇಲಿನ ಆರೋಪವೇ ಹೊರತು ವಾಸ್ತವವಲ್ಲ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಬೌದ್ಧಿಕ ವಲಯದ ವೈದಿಕ ಹಾಗೂ ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯಗಳ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಕಾಣಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ'¹¹.

ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ್ಯದ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತ ಉದಯವಾಯಿತು ಎಂಬ ಆರೋಪಕ್ಕೆ ಪೂರಕವಾದಂತೆ ಹಲವಾರು ಚಿಂತಕರ ವಾದಗಳ ಸರಣಿಯುಗಳನ್ನು ನೋಡುವುದಾದರೆ 'ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ಲೇಖಕರು ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಪೂರ್ವಕವಾಗಿಯೇ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಭಾರತ ಇತಿಹಾಸವನ್ನು ವಿರೂಪಗೊಳಿಸಿ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಮಕ್ಕಳನ್ನು ರಂಜಿಸಲೆಂದು ರಚಿಸಿದ ಕಥೆಯನ್ನಾಗಿ ಭಾರತದ ಇತಿಹಾಸವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇದು ಒಂದೆಡೆಯಾದರೆ ಇಂಡಿಯದ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಇತಿಹಾಸವು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತ ಹಾಗೂ ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥಕ್ಕೂ ನೆಡೆದಿರುವ ಸಂಘರ್ಷವಲ್ಲದೆ ಬೇರೇನೂ ಅಲ್ಲ'¹². ಆದರೆ ಭಾರತದ ಚರಿತ್ರೆಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಬರೆದಿರುವ ಚರಿತ್ರಕಾರರು ಅದನ್ನು ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ ಕಡೆಗಣಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಮತ್ತೇ 'ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತದ ಮೇಲೆ ಜಯಗಳಿಸಿದ್ದಾಗ ಶೂದ್ರರಂತೆ ಮರಳಿ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತವನ್ನು ಬಿಟ್ಟು ಬರಲು ನಿರಾಕರಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದ ಬೌದ್ಧರನ್ನು ಅಶುಭರು ಅನಿಷ್ಟರೆಂದು ಭಾವಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಈ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತವನ್ನು ಬಿಟ್ಟು ಬರಲೋಪ್ಪದ ಕಾರಣಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರು ಚದುರಿಹೋದ ಜನಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಅಸ್ವಶ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರು ಹೇರಿದರು ನಂತರ ಬೌದ್ಧರನ್ನು ಗೋಮಾಂಸ ಭಕ್ಷಕರೆಂದು ತುಚ್ಛೀಕರಿಸಿ ಅವರನ್ನು ಅಗೌರವದಿಂದ ಕಾಣಲಾಯಿತು'¹³. ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರು ಬೌದ್ಧರನ್ನು ತುಚ್ಛವಾಗಿ ಕಾಣಲು ಕಾರಣವೆಂದರೆ 'ವೈದಿಕಪಂಥವನ್ನು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತವು ಪ್ರಧಾನವಾಗಿ ವಿಮರ್ಶಿಸಿದ್ದು ತನ್ನ ಪ್ರಖರ ವಿಚಾರವಾದದ ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪುರೋಹಿತಶಾಹಿಯು ಸುಳ್ಳುಧರ್ಮ ಮತ್ತು ಅಧಿಕೃತ ಧರ್ಮದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತವು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿಯೇ ಮುಂದಿಟ್ಟಿತ್ತು. ವೈದಿಕಪಂಥದ ಸುಳ್ಳು ಪವಾಡಗಳನ್ನು ಅಲೌಕಿಕತೆ ಎಂದು ನಂಬಿಸುವ ಮಟ್ಟಕ್ಕೆ ಇಳಿದಿತ್ತು. ಮೊಳ್ಳು ಪೂಜಾರಿಗಳು ಮೋಸಗಾರ ಮಾಂತ್ರಿಕರನ್ನು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತ ಸುಲಭವಾಗಿ ತನ್ನ ಜೀವನ ನಿಷ್ಠ ಸತ್ಯದ, ತರ್ಕದ ಆಧಾರದಿಂದ ಬಯಲಿಗೆ ಎಳೆಯಿತ್ತು'¹⁴. ಈ ಕಾರಣದಿಂದಲೇ ಬೌದ್ಧರನ್ನು ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರು ತುಚ್ಛವಾಗಿ ಕಾಣಲಾಯಿತು. ಈ

¹⁰ಸಂಶೋಧನಾ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿ, ಸ್ನಾತಕೋತ್ತರ ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಶೋಧನಾ ವಿಭಾಗ, ಕುವೆಂಪು ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ, ಜ್ಞಾನಸಹ್ಯಾದ್ರಿ, ಶಂಕರಘಟ್ಟ, Email: nikhilus234@gmail.com , Phone Number: 7483562456.

¹¹ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನಾ ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಾಗಿ. ಎಸ್. ಎನ್ ಬಾಲಗಂಗಧರ್, (ಅನು. ರಾಜರಾಮ ಹೆಗಡೆ).2010:ಪು.248

¹². ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನಾ ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಾಗಿ ಎಚ್.ಟಿ.ಪೋತೆ,2007:ಪು.3 ನೋಡಿ

¹³. ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನಾ ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಾಗಿ ಮುನಿವಂಕಟಪ್ಪ,2012:ಪು.11,ನೋಡಿ

¹⁴. ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನಾ ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಾಗಿ ಡಾ. ಬಿ. ಆರ್ ಬಾಬಾ ಸಾಹೇಬ್ ಅಂಬೇಡ್ಕರ್ ಬರಹ ಮತ್ತು ಬಹರಗಳು ಸಂಪುಟ-07 ರ ಪುಟ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ 497&492.

ಡಿ. ಆರ್. ನಾಗರಾಜ್,2012:ಪು.23, ಶಿವರಾಮ್,2014:ಪು.144, ಎಚ್. ದಂಡಪ್ಪ,2022.ಪು.432 ನೋಡಿ

ಮೇಲಿನಾ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಗಳು ವಿವರಿಸುವಂತೆ ಅಂತಿಮ ವಿಜಯವು ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರದೇ ಆಯಿತು ಹಿಂದೆಯಿಸಂನ ಅನಿಷ್ಟ ಅಚರಣೆಗಳ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಬಂಡಾಯವೆದ್ದು ಹೊರಾಟದ ಪ್ರತಿಫಲವೇ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತವಾಗಿದೆ. ಹಾಗಾದರೆ ಈ ಮೇಲಿನ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಗಳ ಚಿತ್ರಣವು ವಸ್ತುಸ್ಥಿತಿಯನ್ನಾಧರಿಸಿವೆಯೇ? ಈ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳಿಗನುಗುಣವಾದ ಚಿತ್ರಣವು ಸತ್ಯವಾಗಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಹಿಂದೂಯಿಸಂ ಅಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಯಾವ ಅಂಶಗಳು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತದಲ್ಲಿ ಇರಬಾರದು. ಹಿಂದೂಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯ ಮತ್ತು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ವಿಭಿನ್ನವಾದ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳು ಹಾಗೂ ಅಚರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರಬೇಕು. ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥದ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟತೆಯನ್ನು ವಿರೋಧಿಸಿ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇಯಾದರೆ, ಇವೆರಡೂ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ಭಿನ್ನ ಅಂಶಗಳಿಂದ ರಚನೆಯಾಗಿರಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಇವುಗಳ ಸ್ವರೂಪವನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಅಗತ್ಯ.

ಇದುವರೆಗಿನಾ ವಿದ್ವಾಂಸರು ನೀಡಿರುವ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳಿಗೆ ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾಗಿರುವ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಾವು ಕಾಣಬಹುದು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತಕ್ಕೂ ವೈದಿಕಪಂಥದ ಕೆಲವು ಅಚರಣೆಗಳಿಗೂ ಸಾಮ್ಯತೆಗಳಿದ್ದು, ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಇರುವ ಗ್ರಂಥಗಳಾವುವು ಬುದ್ಧನು ಅವನಾಗಿಯೇ ಬರೆದಿರುವ ಗ್ರಂಥಗಳಲ್ಲ. ಆದರೆ ಅವನ ಶಿಷ್ಯರು ಸಂಗ್ರಹಿಸಿದ ತಾತ್ವಿಕ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನೊಳಗೊಂಡ ಪಾಳಿ ಭಾಷೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಬರೆಯಲಾದ ಗ್ರಂಥವನ್ನು ತ್ರಿಪಿಟಕ ಎಂಬ ಹೆಸರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಕಂಡುಬಂದಿವೆ. ಆ ಬಳಿಕ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತ ಭಾಷೆಯಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇದೇ ಅಂಶವನ್ನು ಹೇಳಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಎಲ್ಲದಕ್ಕಿಂತಲೂ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಶಾಸನಗಳು ಅಶೋಕ ಚಕ್ರವರ್ತಿ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ ಶಾಸನಗಳಾಗಿವೆ. ಅರ್ಥಕಾಲಮರವರು ತಿಳಿಸುವ ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಂಖ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಬರುವ ನಾಲ್ಕು ಮಹಾ ತತ್ವಗಳು ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿರುವ ನಾಲ್ಕು ಯೋಗ ವ್ಯೂಹಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಾಮ್ಯತೆಗಳಿವೆ. ಎಂದು ರಾಘವೇಂದ್ರ ಪೈ ರವರು ಅವರ “ಬೌದ್ಧ ಪಂಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಪತಂಜಲಿಯ ಅಷ್ಟಾಂಗ ಯೋಗ ಸೂತ್ರ ಸಾಮರಸ್ಯ” ಎಂಬ ಲೇಖನದ ಶೀರ್ಷಿಕೆಯ ಅಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಮೊದಲನೆಯ ಸಾಂಖ್ಯ ನಾಲ್ಕು ಮಹಾ ತತ್ವಗಳು ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥ ಪತಂಜಲಿಯ ನಾಲ್ಕು ಯೋಗ ವ್ಯೂಹಗಳು ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಈ ನಾಲ್ಕು ಅದರ್ಶಗಳು ಅರ್ಯಸತ್ಯ ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿವೆ. ಅವುಗಳೆಂದರೆ:

- ದುಃಖ, (ಎಂಬುವುದು ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಅನುಭವಿಸುವ ಯಾತನೆ.)
- ದುಃಖ ಸಮುದಾಯ, (ಯಾತನೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾದ ಹೇತು.)
- ದುಃಖ ನಿರೋಧ, (ಎಂದರೆ ಯಾತನೆಯ ನಿಗ್ರಹ.)
- ದುಃಖ ಮಿನಿ-ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದ. (ಎಂಬುವುದು ದುಃಖ ನಿರೋಧವನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸಲು ಅನುಸರಿಸುವ ಮಾರ್ಗ.)

ಈ ಅಂಶವನ್ನು ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥದ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿರುವ ಪತಂಜಲಿಯ ಯೋಗ ಸೂತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಗಮನಿಸಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದನ್ನೇ ಪತಂಜಲಿಯ ದುಃಖವು ಮೂರು ವಿಧವಾಗಿ ಕಾಣುವುದು. ಅವುಗಳೆಂದರೆ

- ಪರಿಣಾಮ
- ತಾಪ
- ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರ.

ಪತಂಜಲಿಯ ಯೋಗ ಸೂತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಈ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ದಿಕ್ ನಿಖಾಯ ಎಂಬ ಹೆಸರಿನಿಂದ ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ¹⁵. ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ನಂಬಿಕೆ ಅಚರಣೆಗಳು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇದೆ. ಉದಾ: ‘ಬುದ್ಧನು ಆತ್ಮದ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಒಪ್ಪುತ್ತಿರಲಿಲ್ಲವಾದರೂ ಪರಲೋಕ ಪುನರ್ಜನ್ಮಗಳನ್ನು ಒಪ್ಪುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಬರುವ ದೇವ, ಯಕ್ಷ, ಕಿನ್ನರ, ಪ್ರೇತಗಳ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವ ಸರ್ಗ-ನರಕಗಳ ಕಲ್ಪನೆಯನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ದೈವವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ಬೌದ್ಧರು ನಂಬುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು’(ಆಚಾರ್ಯ ನರೇಂದ್ರದೇವ,2022:2).

ವೈದಿಕಪಂಥ ಹೇಗೆ ಬ್ರಹ್ಮ ಜ್ಞಾನಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಋಷಿಮುನಿಗಳು ಆಶ್ರಮದಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ಯಾರಿಗೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣವನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯುವ ಆಸಕ್ತಿ ಇದೆಯೋ ಅವರ ಬಳಿಗೆ ಬಂದು ಶಿಕ್ಷಣಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಇರುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ಅವರಿಗೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣವನ್ನು ಋಷಿಮುನಿಗಳು ನೀಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ಇವರು ಯಾವ ರೀತಿಯ ಆಚಾರ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಪಾಲಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ಆ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಅಂಶಗಳು “ಬೌದ್ಧಮತದ ವೈಖಾನಸ ಸೂತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಿಗುತ್ತವೆ”¹⁶. ಬೌದ್ಧರಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಭಿಕ್ಷುಗಳು ವೈಖಾನಸ ನಿಯಮಗಳನ್ನು ಪಾಲಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ ಅವರನ್ನು ಧುತಂಗನೆಂದು ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ. ವೈದಿಕಪಂಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇಗೆ ಋಷಿಮುನಿಗಳು ಶಿಕ್ಷಣಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಆಶ್ರಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣವನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ಅದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣವನ್ನು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇತ್ತು. ಬೌದ್ಧ ಭಿಕ್ಷು

¹⁵ ದಿನಾಂಕ 2022:7 ಪ್ರಜಾವಾಣಿ ದಿನ ಪತ್ರಿಕೆ ರಾಘವೇಂದ್ರ ಪೈ. ರವರು ‘ಬೌದ್ಧ ಪಂಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಪತಂಜಲಿಯ ಅಷ್ಟಾಂಗ ಯೋಗ ಸೂತ್ರ ಸಾಮರಸ್ಯ’ ಎಂಬ ಲೇಖನದಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಕುರಿತು ಚರ್ಚಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.

¹⁶ ಆಚಾರ್ಯ ನರೇಂದ್ರದೇವ,2022:2.

ಕ್ಷೇಶವನ್ನು ಕಳೆದ ಮೇಲೆ ಪರಿಶುದ್ಧನಾಗಿ ನಂತರ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣವನ್ನು ನೀಡುವವರಿಗೆ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತದಲ್ಲಿ ದುತಂಗರೆಂದು ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು.

ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಮನಸ್ಸನ್ನು ಶಾಂತಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಬೌದ್ಧ ಹಾಗೂ ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಅನೇಕ ಪ್ರಯೋಗಗಳಿವೆ. 'ದೇಹವನ್ನು ಅಶುಭ ಅಶುಚಿ ಎಂದು ತಿಳಿಯುವುದು ಅಶುಭ ಸಂಜ್ಞೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಆನಾಪಾನ ಸ್ಮೃತಿ ಪ್ರಾಣಾಯಾಮದ ಪ್ರಯೋಗ, ಮಾಡುವುದರಿಂದ ರಾಗಾನುಶಯ ನಾಶವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಕಾಮ ಮತ್ತು ಮನಸ್ಸು ಪ್ರಕ್ಷಬ್ಧಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಕರ್ಮಸ್ಥಾನದಿಂದ ಭಾವನೆಯಿಂದ ಪಾಪ ಅಕುಶಲ ಧರ್ಮಗಳು ಹೇಗೆ ಹುಟ್ಟುತ್ತವೆಯೋ ಹಾಗೇ ಮಯಾವಾಗುತ್ತವೆ. ಎಂದು ಬುದ್ಧನು ಇವುಗಳನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಪ್ರಶಂಸೆ ಮಾಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇದು ಚಿತ್ತ(ಮನಸ್ಸು) ಸಹಜವಾಗಿ ಶಾಂತ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಣೀತವಾಗಿಡಲು ಸಹಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. ದ್ವೇಷಾಗ್ನಿಯಾ ಉಪಶಮನಕ್ಕೆ ತಪಸ್ಸು ಒಂದು ದೊಡ್ಡ ಕಾಂತ್ರಿ ಎಂದು ಬುದ್ಧ ಹೇಳುತ್ತಾನೆ. ಸರ್ವರೂ ಸುಖಿಯಾಗಿರಲಿ; ಸರ್ವರಿಗೂ ಕಲ್ಯಾಣವಾಗಲಿ ಎಂದು ಮೈತ್ರಿ ಭಾವನೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಯಾರು ಪ್ರಾರ್ಥನೆ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಅವರು ಎಲ್ಲಾ ದಿಕ್ಕುಗಳನ್ನು ಮೈತ್ರಿಯಿಂದ ಕೂಡಿದ ಮನಸ್ಸಿನಿಂದ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಮೈತ್ರಿ ಭಾವವು ನಾಲ್ಕು ಬ್ರಹ್ಮ ವಿಹಾರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಾಗಿದೆ. ಮಿಕ್ಕ ಬ್ರಹ್ಮ ವಿಹಾರಗಳು ಮುದಿತಾ, ಕರುಣೆ, ಮತ್ತು ಉಪೇಕ್ಷಾಗಳಾಗಿವೆ. ಇವುಗಳ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖ ಯೋಗಸೂತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿವೆ¹⁷. ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥ ದಲ್ಲಿ ನಾಲ್ಕು ಆಶ್ರಮಗಳಿರುವ ಕಥೆಯಿದೆ, ಅದೇ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ನಾಲ್ಕು ಆಶ್ರಮಗಳಿವೆ. ಬ್ರಹ್ಮಚಾರ್ಯವನ್ನು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತದಲ್ಲಿ ಶ್ರಮಣೋರ ಎಂಥಲೂ, ಗೃಹಸ್ಥನನ್ನು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತದಲ್ಲಿ ಗೃಹಪತಿ, ವಾಸಪ್ರಸ್ಥನನ್ನು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಿಕ್ಷುವೆಂಥಲೂ, ಋಷಿಮುನಿಗಳನ್ನು ಅರಣ್ಯಕ ಎಂಥಲೂ, ಒಂದೇ ರೀತಿಯಾದಂತಹ ಆಶ್ರಮಗಳ ಆಚರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಬೌದ್ಧ ಹಾಗೂ ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥ ಎರಡರಲ್ಲೂ ನಾವು ಒಂದೇ ರೀತಿಯಾ ಆಚರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಾವು ಕಾಣಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

ಮುಂದುವರೆದು ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸಂವಾದಗಳಿದ್ದು. ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಂಡಿದೆ ಅಗಿದ್ದಲ್ಲಿ. ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಯೇ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬಾರದಿತ್ತು. ಆದರೆ ಬುದ್ಧ ಸೋನದಂಡನ ಜೊತೆಗಿನಾ ಸಮವಾದದಲ್ಲಿ ನಿಜವಾದ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣನಾರು ಎಂಬ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಯನ್ನು ಇಟ್ಟುಕೊಂಡು ಜಿಜ್ಞಾಸೆ ನಡೆಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಬುದ್ಧನಿಗೆ ಸ್ವತಃ ಆರೋಪಿಸಲಾದೊಂದು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಠ್ಯವಾದ ಧಮ್ಮಪದ, ಮತ್ತು ಎರಡನೆಯದು ಬುದ್ಧನಾ ಸಂಭಾಷಣೆಯನ್ನು ದಾಖಲಿಸುವ ಒಂದು ಉಪಪಠ್ಯವಾದ ಸೋನದಂಡ ಸುತ್ತ. ಹಾಗೂ ಧಮ್ಮಪದದ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣವಗ್ಗೆ ಎಂಬ ಕೊನೆಯ ಅಧ್ಯಾಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ಕುರಿತಾಗಿ ಈ ರೀತಿಯ ವಿವರಣೆಯಿದೆ.

“ಜಟಿಯಿಂದಲ್ಲ, ಗೋತ್ರದಿಂದಲ್ಲ, ಹುಟ್ಟಿನಿಂದಲೂ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣನಾಗುದಿಲ್ಲ ಸತ್ಯ ಧರ್ಮ ಯಾರಲ್ಲಿದೆಯೋ ಅವನೇ ಶುದ್ಧ ಅವನೇ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ. ಯಾರು ಕೇವಲ ಗರ್ಭ ಸಂಜಾತನೋ, ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ತಾಯಿಗೆ ಹುಟ್ಟಿದನೋ ಅವನು ಕೇವಲ 'ಭೋ' ಎನ್ನುವವರು ಸಂಪತ್ತಿನಾ ಒಡೆಯನಾಗಿದ್ದರೆ ಅವನು ಅಂಥವ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣನೆನ್ನುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಏನೂ ಇಲ್ಲದ ಏನನ್ನೂ ಒಲ್ಲದ ನರನೇ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣನೆನ್ನುವೆನು. ಯಾರು ಇಹ ಸಂಬಂಧವ ತ್ಯಜಿಸಿದನೋ, ಸ್ವರ್ಗದ ಬಂಧನ ದಾಟಿದನೋ ಯಾರು ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಬಂಧನ ಹಳಚಿದನೋ ಅವನೇ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣನೆನ್ನುವೆನು” (ಎಸ್. ಎನ್. ಬಾಲಗಂಗಾಧರ್, 2010:248). ಒಂದು ವೇಳೆ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ಮತ್ತು ಅವರ ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥದ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ನಡೆದ ಚಳವಳಿಯಾಗಿದ್ದರೆ, ಬುದ್ಧ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ಎಂದರೆ ಯಾರು? ಎಂಬ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಯೇ ಕೇಳಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬಾರದಿತ್ತು. ಆದರೆ ಬುದ್ಧ ಸೋನದಂಡನ ಜೊತೆ ನಿಜವಾದ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣನಾರು ಎಂಬ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಯನ್ನು ಇಟ್ಟುಕೊಂಡು ಜಿಜ್ಞಾಸೆ ನಡೆಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಈ ರೀತಿಯ ಜಿಜ್ಞಾಸೆಯನ್ನೇ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ನಡೆದ ಚಳವಳಿ ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯುವುದಾದರೆ ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥದ ಭಾಗವೆಂದು ಕರೆಯಲ್ಪಡುವ ಮಹಾಭಾರತದ ಉದ್ದಕ್ಕೂ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರೆಂದರೆ ಯಾರು? ಎಂಬ ಅಜಗರ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗೆ ಯುಧಿಷ್ಠಿರನ ಉತ್ತರವು ಹೀಗೆ ಇದೆ. 'ಸತ್ಯ, ದಾನ, ಕ್ಷಮಾ, ಶೀಲ, ಉದಾರತೆ, ತಪಸ್ಸು ಹಾಗೂ ದಯೆ ಇವೆಲ್ಲವೂ ಯಾವನಲ್ಲಿರುತ್ತವೆಯೋ ಅವನೇ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣನೆನಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾನೆ. ಅವನು ಸುಖ ದುಃಖಗಳನ್ನು ದಾಟಿದ ಪರ ಬ್ರಹ್ಮ ವಸ್ತುವನ್ನು ತಿಳಿದವನಾಗಿರುತ್ತಾನೆ. ಶೂದ್ರನಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಈ ಗುಣಗಳಿದ್ದರೆ ಅವನು ಶೂದ್ರನಾಗುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣನಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಗುಣಗಳಿಲ್ಲದಿದ್ದರೆ ಅವನು ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣನಾಗುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಈ ಗುಣಗಳು ಇರುವವನೇ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣನೆನಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾನೆ ಅವನು ಶೂದ್ರನಾದರೂ'¹⁸ ಎಂಬ ಜಿಜ್ಞಾಸೆ ಕಾಣಬಹುದು. ಹಾಗದರೆ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತದ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಇರುವ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಇರುವ ವಿವರಣೆಗೂ ಮಹಾಭಾರತದ ವನಪರ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಬರುವ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಇರುವ ವಿವರಣೆಗೂ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸವಿಲ್ಲ. ಅಂದರೆ ಮಹಾಭಾರತವು ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ಜಾತಿಯ ವಿರುದ್ಧವೇ? ಎಂಬ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೇ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಸಹಜ. ಯಾಕೆಂದರೆ ಇದೆ. ರೀತಿಯ ವಿವರಣೆಯನ್ನು ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವೆಂದೆಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಧಮ್ಮ ಪದದ ಕೊನೆಯಾ ಅಧ್ಯಾಯದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ವಿವರಣೆಯನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬಹುದು. ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿರುವ ಧಮ್ಮಪದದ ಕೊನೆಯ

¹⁷ ಅದೇ,ಪು.13

¹⁸ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನಾ ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಾಗಿ ಪಶ್ಚಿಮಾಯಾನ ರಾಜಾರಾಮ ಹೆಗಡೆ.2022:46 ಅಧುನಿಕ ಜಾತಿ ಮೀಮಾಂಸೆ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಾಭಾರತದ ಸಂವಾದಗಳು ಎಂಬ ಲೇಖನದಲ್ಲಿ ಚರ್ಚಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.

ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣವಗ್ಗ ಅಧ್ಯಾಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಇರುವ ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿದ್ದಾಗ ಬುದ್ಧ ಮತ್ತು ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ಎರಡನ್ನು ಒಂದೇ ಅರ್ಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಸಿರುವುದು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟ.

ಉದಾ: “ಅಲಂಕಟೋ ಚ ಪಿ ಸಮಜ್ ಚರಯ್ಯ

ಸಂತೋ ದಂತೋ ನಿಯತೋ ಬ್ರಹ್ಮಚಾರೀ

ಸಬ್ಬೇಸು ಭೂತೇಸು ನಿಧಾಯ ದಂಡಜ್

ಸೋ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣೋ, ಸೋ ಸಮಣೋ, ಸಾ ಭಿಕ್ಷು” (ಧಮ್ಮಪದ).

ಅಲಂಕಾರವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದರೂ ಶಮವನ್ನು ಯಾರು ಆಚರಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿಟ್ಟಿರುವನೋ, ಶಾಂತನಾಗಿ ದಾಂತನಾಗಿ ನಿಯಮವಂತನಾಗಿ ಬ್ರಹ್ಮಚಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಯಾವ ಪ್ರಾಣಿಯನ್ನು ದಂಡಿಸದೆ ಯಾರು ಇರುವನೋ ಅವನೇ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ, ಅವನೇ ಶ್ರಮಣ, ಅವನೇ ಭೀಕ್ಷು. (ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ, ಶ್ರಮಣ, ಭಿಕ್ಷು = ಪವಿತ್ರವಾದವನು, ಎಲ್ಲವನ್ನೂ ತ್ಯಜಿಸಿದವನು, ಸಂನ್ಯಾಸಿ)

ಖಂತೀಪರಮಜ್ ಕಪೋತಿತಿಕ್ಖಾ

ನಿಭ್ಭಾಂಜ್ ಪರಮಜ್ ವದಂತಿಬುದ್ಧಾ

ನ ಹಿ ಪಬ್ಬಜಿತೋಪರೂಪ ಘಾತಿ

ಸಮಣೋಹೋತಿಪರಜ್ ವಿಹೇಥಯಂತೋ (ಧಮ್ಮಪದ).

ಕ್ಖಾಂತಿಯೇ (ಮಹಾ ತಾಳೆ) ದೊಡ್ಡ ತಪಸ್ಸು, ತಿತಿಕ್ಷಯೇ ಮಹಾ ಸಮಾಧಾನ ದೊಡ್ಡ ನಿರ್ವಾಣ ಎಂದು ತಿಳಿದವರು ಹೇಳುವರು ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಮತ್ತೋಬ್ಬರನ್ನು ಕೊಲ್ಲುವವನು ಸನ್ಯಾಸಿಯಲ್ಲ. ಮತ್ತೋಬ್ಬರನ್ನು ಸಂಕಟಗೊಳಿಸುವವನು ಶ್ರಮಣನಲ್ಲ.

ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದ ಕೊನೆಯ ಅಧ್ಯಾಯವಾದ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ವಗ್ಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಗವನ್ ಬುದ್ಧನು ಸಂಭಾಷಣೆ ಎನ್ನಲಾದ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಈ ಮೇಲಿನಾ ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟ ಪಡಿಸುವಂತೆ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತದಲ್ಲಿ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಇರುವಂತ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳು ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಬರುವಂತಹ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಇರುವಂತಹ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳು ಎರಡು ಒಂದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳೆಂದು ಈ ಮೇಲಿನಾ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಗಳಿಂದ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿದೆ. ಅದರೂ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣಶಾಯಿಯ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಬಂಡಾಯವೆಂದು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತ ಉದಯವಾಯಿತು. ಎಂಬ ಯಾವ ಆಧಾರವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಬಲವಾಗಿ ಇಟ್ಟುಕೊಟ್ಟು ಹೀಗೆ ಮಾತನಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಒಂದು ವೇಳೆ ಟೀಕೆ ಟಿಪ್ಪಣಿಗಳನ್ನು ಗುರಿಯಾಗಿಸಿ ಮಾತನಾಡಿದರೆ. ಭಾರತೀಯ ಮತ ಪಂಥ ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಹಜವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ಮತ್ತು ಶ್ರಮಣ ಇವರಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ವಾಭಾವಿಕವಾಗಿ ಟೀಕೆಗಳು ಇದ್ದವು.

ಉದಾ: ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರು ತಲೆ ಬೋಳಿಸಿಕೊಂಡವರ ದರ್ಶನವನ್ನು ಅಶುಭವೆಂದು ಭಾವಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರು ಸರ್ವಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಗೃಹಸ್ಥರಾಗುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ಶ್ರಮಣರು ಬ್ರಹ್ಮಚಾರ್ಯವನನ್ನು ಪಾಲಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರು ಸತ್ಯಾ ಅನ್ವೇಷಣೆಗಾಗಿ ಒಬ್ಬ ಆಚಾರ್ಯರ ಬಳಿ ಇರುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ಶ್ರಮಣರು ತಮ್ಮ ಗಣ ಅಥವಾ ಸಂಘ ಸೇರುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರು ಪಾಪ ಪುಣ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಕರ್ಮದ-ಫಲದಲ್ಲಿ ನಂಬಿಕೆಯಿಟ್ಟಿದ್ದರು. ಶ್ರಮಣರು ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯಗಳು ತಪಸ್ಸಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನಾ ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ವೈದಿಕಶಾಯಿಯ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಅಂತ ಹೇಳುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ಯಾವ ಯಾವ ಹೇಳಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಎತ್ತಿ ತರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ವೇದಗಳ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನವಾದ ಅದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ಹೇಳಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಮಹಾ ಭಾರತ ಉಪನಿಷತ್ತಿನಲ್ಲಿ ವೇದಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಒಂದೇ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿದೆ. ಅದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಗಳು ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇದೆ. ಒಂದು ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಟೀಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಇಟ್ಟು ಕೊಂಡು ವಿರೋಧಿ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳುವುದಾದರೆ. ವೇದಗಳು ಮಹಾಭಾರತ, ಉಪನಿಷತ್ತು, ವಚನ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯ, ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ವಿರೋಧಿ ಅಂತ ಹೇಳಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಆ ಹೇಳಿಕೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾವ ರೀತಿಯ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸಗಳು ಇಲ್ಲ. ಯಾಕೆಂದರೆ ಅಧ್ಯಾತ್ಮಿಕ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ಅಥವಾ ಲೌಕಿಕಾ, ಅಧ್ಯಾತ್ಮಿಕ ವಿಷಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಏನು ಟೀಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿದರೋ ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಟೀಕೆಗಳು ಎರಡಲೂ ಇದೆ. ಆ ಟೀಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಇಟ್ಟುಕೊಂಡು ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣಶಾಯಿ ಪುರೋಹಿತಶಾಯಿ ವಿರೋಧಿ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳುವುದಾದರೆ ಇಡೀ ವೇದ, ಮಹಾಭಾರತ, ಉಪನಿಷತ್ತು, ವಚನ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯ ಪುರೋಹಿತಶಾಯಿ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಅಂತ ಹೇಳಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಚಿಂತಕರುಗಳು ಹೇಗೆ ತಾರ್ಕಿಕವಾದ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಯನ್ನು ಮುಂದೆ ಇಡುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಈ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆ ತಾರ್ಕಿಕ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆ ಯಾವ ಯಾವ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಯನ್ನು ಇಟ್ಟುಕೊಂಡು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತ ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯ ವೇದ ವಿರೋಧಿ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ವಿರೋಧಿ ಪುರೋಹಿತಶಾಯಿ ವಿರೋಧಿ ಅಂತ ಹೇಳುತ್ತಾರೋ ಅದೇ ರೀತಿಯಾ ಹೇಳಿಕೆಗಳು ವೇದಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇದೆ. ಉಪನಿಷತ್ತಿನಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇದೆ. ಭಗವತ್ ಗೀತೆಯಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇದೆ. ರಾಮಾಯಣ ಮಹಾಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇದೆ. ಹಾಗಾದರೆ ಏನು ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸ ಮಹಾ ಭಾರತ ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯಕ್ಕೂ ಏನೂ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯ ಹೇಗೆ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ವಿರೋಧಿ ಅಂತ ಹೇಳುವುದಾದರೆ. ಉಪನಿಷತ್ತು, ವೇದ, ಭಗವತ್ ಗೀತೆ, ಮಹಾಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅದೇ ರೀತಿ ವಿವರಣೆ ಇದೆ. ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ವಿರೋಧಿ ಅಂತ ಹೇಳಬಹುದಲ್ಲ.

ಒಂದು ವೇಳೆ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತ ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥದ ವಿರೋಧಿ ಅಥವಾ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣಶಾಯಿ ವಿರೋಧಿ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳುವುದಾದರೆ ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದ ಕೊನೆಯ ಅಧ್ಯಾಯದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವರಿಸಿರುವಂತೆ ಭಗವಾನ್ ಬುದ್ಧರೇ ಹೇಳುವಂತೆ ‘ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ಎಂದರೆ ಯಾರು?’ ಎಂಬ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗೆ ಉತ್ತರವನ್ನೇ ನೀಡಬಾರದಿತ್ತು. ನೀಡಿದ್ದರು ಬುದ್ಧನು ನೀಡಿರುವ ವಿವರಣೆಗೂ ವೈದಿಕ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದ ವಿವರಣೆಗೂ ಭಿನ್ನತೆಯಿಂದಾ ಇರಬೇಕಾಗಿತ್ತು.

ಆದರೆ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳು ಭಿನ್ನತೆಯಿಂದ ಕೂಡಿಲ್ಲ. ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ಪುರೋಹಿತಶಾಖೆಯ ವಿರುದ್ಧವೇ ನಡೆದ ಹೋರಾಟವಾಗಿದ್ದರೆ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ಎಂದರೆ ಯಾರು ಎಂಬ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಯೇ ಬರಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಿಲ್ಲ. ಮತ್ತು ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ವಿರೋಧಿಯಾದ ಪಕ್ಷದಲ್ಲಿ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ವೈದಿಕ ಪಂಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಬರುವ ವಿವರಣೆಗೂ ಮತ್ತು ಬೌದ್ಧಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದ ವಿವರಣೆಗೂ ಸಾಮ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಕಾಣಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯತೆಯೇ ಇರಲಿಲ್ಲ. ಹಿಂದೂಯಿಸಂ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತವು ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಂಡಿದೇ ಅದಲ್ಲ. ಹಿಂದೂಯಿಸಂನಾ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿರುವ ಉಪನಿಷತ್ತು, ವೇದ, ಯೋಗ, ಮಹಾಭಾರತ ಇವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿನಾ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳಿಗೂ ಬೌದ್ಧಮತದಲ್ಲಿನಾ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳಿಗೂ ಸಾಮ್ಯತೆ ಹೇಗೆ ಸಾಧ್ಯ? ಎಂಬ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆ ಸಹಜವಾಗಿ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಹಿಂದೂಯಿಸಂ ಹಾಗೂ ಬುದ್ಧಿಸಂ ಎರಡರಲ್ಲೂ ಸಾಮ್ಯತೆ ಇರುವುದರಿಂದ ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ್ಯವನ್ನು ಎತ್ತಿ ಹಿಡಿಯುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂಬ ಅರ್ಥ ಬರುತ್ತದೆಯೇ ಹೊರತು ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ್ಯದ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ನಿರಾಕರಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳುವುದು ಸತ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ದೂರವಾದ ಮಾತು...

ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆಯಾಗಿ ಬೌದ್ಧಿಕ ವಲಯದ ಚಿಂತನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾವ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಇಟ್ಟುಕೊಂಡು ಬೌದ್ಧಮತವು ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣರ ವಿರೋಧಿ ಎನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೋ ಆ ಅಂಶಗಳು ಟೀಕೆಗಳೇ ಹೊರತು ವಿರೋಧವಲ್ಲ. ಒಂದು ವೇಳೆ ಟೀಕೆಗಳನ್ನೇ ವಿರೋಧವೆನ್ನುವುದಾದರೆ ಭಾರತೀಯಾ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಮತ ಪಂಥ ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನಾವು ಟೀಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬಹುದು. ಈ ಟೀಕೆಗಳನ್ನೇ ಇಟ್ಟುಕೊಂಡು ವಿರೋಧ ಎಂಬ ಹೇಳಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡುವುದಾದರೆ ಲಿಂಗಾಯತಿಸಂ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ವೀರಶೈವ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಂಡಿತು. ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣಿಸಂ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಬುದ್ಧಿಸಂ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಂಡಿತು. ಹಿಂದುಹಿಸಂ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಜೈನಿಸಂ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಂಡಿತ್ತು ಎಂಬ ಹೇಳಿಕೆಗಳು ವಿವರಣೆಗಳು ಬೆಳೆಯುತ್ತವೆಯೇ ಹೊರತು ಭಾರತೀಯಾ ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯ ಮತ ಪಂಥಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆನಾ ನಿಜವಾದ ಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಕಟ್ಟಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಿಲ್ಲ.

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ಅಂಬೇಡ್ಕರ್. ಬಿ. ಆರ್, (2015). ಡಾ. ಬಾಬಾಸಾಹೇಬ್ ಅಂಬೇಡ್ಕರ್ ಬರಹಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಭಾಷಣಗಳು, ಸಂ. 19. ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು: ಕನ್ನಡ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ ನಿರ್ದೇಶನಾಲಯ.

ಭಾರತದ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳು ಒಂದು ವಿಮರ್ಶಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ

ಶ್ರೀ ಶಿವರಾಮಯ್ಯ

ಸಹ ಪ್ರಾಧ್ಯಾಪಕರು

ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ವಿಭಾಗ

ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಪ್ರಥಮ ದರ್ಜೆ ಕಾಲೇಜು, ಕೊರಟಗೆರೆ.

ಪಿರೀಕೆ

ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವು ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳ ಸರ್ಕಾರವಾಗಿದ್ದು ಸಾರ್ವಭೌಮ ಸಮಾಜವಾದಿ ಸರ್ವಧರ್ಮ ಸಮಭಾವ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಗಣರಾಜ್ಯವಾದ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಜನಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಇರುತ್ತದೆ ಈ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಸಂವಿಧಾನವು 15ನೇ ಭಾಗದ ವಿಧಿ 324 ರಿಂದ 329 ರ ವರೆಗೆ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗಕ್ಕೆ ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ಶಾಶ್ವತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಾತ್ಮಕ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು ಸಾವಿರದ ಒಂಬೈನೂರ ಐವತ್ತು ಜನವರಿ 26ರಂದು ಜಾರಿಗೆ ಬಂದ ಮೂಲ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ನಮೂದಿಸಿರುವುದು ಕಾಣಬಹುದು ಈ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಕಮಿಷನರ್ ಮತ್ತು ಇತರೆ ಇಬ್ಬರು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಕಮಿಷನರಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇವರನ್ನು 324ರ ಎರಡನೇ ಉಪವಿಧಿ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ನೇಮಿಸುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಪತಿಯವರಿಗಿದೆ 1950 ರಿಂದ 1993 ರವರೆಗೆ ಏಕ ಸದಸ್ಯತ್ವ ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದು ಆಯೋಗವು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತದಲ್ಲಿ ತ್ರಿಸದ ಶತ್ರು ವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಪತಿ ಉಪರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಪತಿ ಲೋಕಸಭೆ, ರಾಜ್ಯಸಭೆ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆ ವಿಧಾನಪರಿಷತ್ತಿನ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ 1992 ರಲ್ಲಿ ನಂತರ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳ ಹಾಗೂ ನಗರ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ರಾಜ್ಯ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗಕ್ಕಿದೆ

ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರವಾಗಿ ನಿರ್ಭೀತಿಯಿಂದ ಮತ್ತು ಯಾವುದೇ ಪಕ್ಷಪಾತ ಮಾಡದೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನಡೆಸುವುದಾಗಿದೆ ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರವನ್ನು ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಬದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗಕ್ಕೆ ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು ಮತದಾರರ ಪಟ್ಟಿ ತಯಾರಿಸುವುದು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳಿಗೆ ಮಾನ್ಯತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಚಿಹ್ನೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡುವುದು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ನೀತಿ ಸಮಿತಿ ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸುವುದು ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಮತದಾರರ ಗುರುತಿನ ಚೀಟಿ ನೀಡುವುದು ಮತಪತ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಮತಯಂತ್ರದ ಬಳಕೆ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಅರ್ಹತೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಅನರ್ಹತೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸುವುದು ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಮರು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಮಧ್ಯಂತರ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವುದು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಮುಂದೂಡುವ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಅಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ತಡೆಗಟ್ಟುವುದು ಮುಂತಾದ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು ನಿಭಾಯಿಸುವುದು

1951 ರ ಪ್ರಜಾ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಅನ್ವಯ ಅನೇಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನೀತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ನಿಯಮಗಳು ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಬಂದಿದೆ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಮತದಾನವನ್ನು 1989 ರಲ್ಲಿ 61ನೇ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಮತದಾನ ವಯಸ್ಸನ್ನು 21ರಿಂದ 18 ವರ್ಷಕ್ಕೆ ಇಳಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಇದರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ 18 ವರ್ಷ ತುಂಬಿದ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬರು 324ನೇ ವಿಧಿ ಇದರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಮತದಾನಕ್ಕೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ ಹಾಗೂ ನಾಮಪತ್ರ ಪರಿಶೀಲನೆಗಾಗಿ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಹೆಸರು ಅಧಿಕೃತವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಕಟ ಯಾಗುವರೆಗೂ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿ ಲೋಕಸಭೆಗೆ 25,000 ರಾಜ್ಯ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆಗೆ 10,000 ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿ ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ವರ್ಗದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಲೋಕಸಭೆಗೆ

12,500 ಗಳು ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆಗೆ 5000 ರೂಗಳನ್ನು ಠೇವಣಿ ಹಣ ನೀಡಬೇಕು ಹಾಗೂ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಗಳು ಸ್ವಯಂ ಆಸ್ತಿ ಘೋಷಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು

ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ನಾಮಪತ್ರ ನಾಮಪತ್ರ ವಾಪಸ್ಸು ಪಡೆದ ಯಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಯುವ ದಾಖಲೆ ಬೂತ್ ಕಳವು ಮತ್ತು ಮತದಾನಕ್ಕೆ ಅಡ್ಡಪಡಿಸುವುದರ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಕ್ರಮ ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ ಚಲಾವಣೆಯಾದ ಒಟ್ಟು ಮತಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಮತ ಯಾರ ಪರವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆಯೋ ಅಂತಹವರನ್ನು ಜಯಗಳಿಸಿದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯೆಂದು ತೀರ್ಮಾನಿಸಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಆರನೇ ಒಂದರಷ್ಟು ಅಥವಾ ಅದಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮತ ಗಳಿಸಿದರೆ ಆಯೋಗವು ಠೇವಣಿ ಹಣವನ್ನು ಹಿಂದಿರುಗಿಸುವಂತಿಲ್ಲ

ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸವಾಲುಗಳು

ಭಾರತವು ವಿಶ್ವದಲ್ಲೇ ಬೃಹತ್ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಹೊಂದಿದ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾಗಿದೆ ನಮ್ಮ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯನ್ನು ವಿಶ್ವ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಅರ್ಥದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವರಿಸಿರುವುದು ಕಾಣುತ್ತೇವೆ ಆದರೂ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳು ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡುವ ಅವಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅನೇಕ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಅಂತಹ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲವನ್ನು ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾಣಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ

1. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಮುಖಂಡರು ಮತ್ತು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಅವಾಚ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಅನಾವಶ್ಯಕ ಶಬ್ದಗಳ ಬಳಕೆಯಿಂದ ಇಕ್ಕಟ್ಟಿನ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಉಂಟುಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ.
2. ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಅಕ್ರಮಗಳು ಮತಗಟ್ಟೆಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ದಾಳಿ ಮತಪತ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಮತಯಂತ್ರಗಳ ಭಾಷಾ ಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಾಮಾಣಿಕ ಮತದಾರರಿಗೆ ತೊಡಕು ಮಾಡುವುದು
3. ಹಣ ಹೆಂಡ ಸೀರೆ ವಾಚು ಉಡುಗೊರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಇತರ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಮತದಾರರಿಗೆ ಒಡ್ಡುವುದು
4. ನಾಯಿ ಕೊಡೆಗಳಂತೆ ದಿನೇ ದಿನೇ ಬೆಳೆಯುತ್ತಿರುವ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು
5. ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಾಗಿ ಕೋಟ್ಯಂತರ ರೂಪಾಯಿಯನ್ನು ಅನಾವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿ ಬಯಸುತ್ತಿರುವುದು
6. ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ ಅನಾವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗುತ್ತಿರುವುದು
7. ಮತದಾರರ ಪಟ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಸರು ನಾಪತ್ತೆಯಾಗುವುದು
8. ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಠೇವಣಿ ಹಣ ಕಡಿಮೆಯಾಗಿರುವುದು
9. ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ದುಂದು ವೆಚ್ಚವನ್ನು ನಿಯಂತ್ರಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗದಿರುವುದು
10. ಒಬ್ಬ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯೇ ಎರಡು ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವುದು
11. ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಬಹುತೇಕ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಬೇರೆ ಬೇರೆ ಅವಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಯುವುದು
12. ಮತದಾರರು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಆಸಕ್ತಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ ನಗರ ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ಮತದಾರರಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರಾಸಕ್ತಿ ಮೂಡುತ್ತಿರುವುದು
13. ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಕ್ರಿಮಿನಲ್ ಮುಖದ್ವಮೆಗಳನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿ ಜಯಗಳಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವುದು
14. ನಕಲಿ ಮತದಾನ ಕಂಡು ಬರುತ್ತಿರುವುದು
15. ಮಹಿಳೆಯರಿಗೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯತೆ ಇಲ್ಲದಿರುವುದು
16. ಸಜನ ಪಕ್ಷಪಾತವಿರುವ ಪಕ್ಷ ವರಿಷ್ಠರು ಇರುವುದು
17. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಶಕ್ತಿ ಸಂಘಟನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹಾಗೂ ಇತರ ಸಂಘಟನೆಗಳನ್ನು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಹಣ ನೀಡಿ ಪ್ರಚಾರ ಕಾರ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿರುವುದು
18. ಪಕ್ಷಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಆಂತರಿಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಇಲ್ಲದೆ ಇರುವುದು

19. ಸ್ವಜನಾ ಪಕ್ಷಪಾತವಿರುವ ಪಕ್ಷ ವರಿಷ್ಠರು ಇರುವುದು

ಹೀಗೆ ಹಲವಾರು ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಇನ್ನೂ ಹೊಸ ರೀತಿಯ ಹಲವಾರು ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಆಯೋಗವು ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ

ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸುಧಾರಣೆ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆ =-

ಅಬ್ಬರದ ಪ್ರಚಾರ ನಕಲಿ ಮತದಾನ ಜಾತಿ ಪರಿಗಣನೆ ಹಣ ಹೆಂಡಗಳ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಅಪರಾಧಿಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುವಂತಿದೆನಮ್ಮ ದೇಶದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯು ಮತಯಂತ್ರ ಕಬ್ಬಳಕ್ಕೆ ಮತದಾರರಿಗೆ ಗುರುತಿನ ಚೀಟಿ ಅಷ್ಟೇ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಮತ್ತು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾಪಿಸಿದಾಗಲೆಲ್ಲ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗಳು ನಕಲಿ ಮತದಾನ ಅಬ್ಬರದ ಪ್ರಚಾರ ನನ್ನ ಹೆಸರು ಸುಪ್ರೀಂ ಕೋರ್ಟ್ ತಜ್ಞರು ನೀಡಿದ ಸಲಹೆ ಸೂಚನೆಗಳು ಯಾವ ಲೆಕ್ಕಕ್ಕೆ ಬಾರದೆ ಹೋಗಿವೆ. ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಆದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಅವುಗಳ ಜಾರಿ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗದ ಮಾರ್ಗದರ್ಶಿ ಸೂತ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ಸರ್ವ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಸಾರಾ ಸಾಗುಟಾಗಿ ತಿರಸ್ಕರಿಸುತ್ತಾ ಬಂದಿದೆ ಅವಧಿ ಮುಗಿಯುವ ಮೊದಲೇ ನಡೆಯುವ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಿಂದ ಅರ್ಥವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ದುಷ್ಪರಿಣಾಮ ಉಂಟಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆದರೆ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ವೆಚ್ಚ ಕಪ್ಪು ಹಣದ ಮೇಲಿನ ಅವಲಂಬನೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅವಹಾರಗಳು ಕಡಿಮೆಯಾಗುತ್ತವೆ. ಕೋಟಿಗಟ್ಟಲೆ ಕುಟುಂಬಗಳು ಬಡತನ ರೇಖೆಯ ಕೆಳಗೆ ಇರುವ ನಮ್ಮ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಪದೇಪದೇ ನಡೆಯಬಾರದು ಐದು ವರ್ಷಗಳಿಗೊಮ್ಮೆ ನಡೆಯುವ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಖರ್ಚು ಮಾಡಬಾರದು ಎಂಬುದು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗದ ಆದ್ಯ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ

1. ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕಪ್ಪು ಹಣದ ಹಾವಳಿಗೆ ಹೀಗಿರುವ ಕಾನೂನು ಚೌಕಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಕಡಿವಾಣ ಹಾಕುವುದು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಿಲ್ಲ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹರಿಯುತ್ತಿರುವ ಹಣದ ಹೊಳೆ ದೊಡ್ಡ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯಾಗಿದೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹರಿಯುತ್ತಿರುವ ಹಣದ ಹೊಳೆ ದೊಡ್ಡ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯಾಗಿದೆ ಹಣಕಾಸು ವಿಚಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆ ತರುವ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಬಹಳ ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳು ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಿವೆ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಸುಗಮವಾಗಿ ನಡೆಯಲು ಧೈರ್ಯ ನಡತೆ ಸಮಗ್ರತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಜ್ಞಾನದ ಸಂಪತ್ತು ಅವಶ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ ಆದರೆ ಇಂದು ಇವೆಲ್ಲವೂ ಕುಸಿತಕಾ ಹಾದಿಯಲ್ಲಿದ್ದು ಇವುಗಳನ್ನು ಸುಧಾರಿಸುವುದು ಇಂದಿನ ಆಧ್ಯ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ

2. ನೋಟ ಪರಿಹಾರವಲ್ಲ ಮಾತುಕತೆಯ ಮೂಲಕ ನ್ಯಾಯ ಸಮ್ಮತವಾದ ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ವ ಸಮ್ಮತವಾಗಿ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಅವಕಾಶಗಳಿವೆ ಅಂತೆಯೇ ನಮ್ಮ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಈಡೇರಿಸದ ನಾಯಕರನ್ನು ತಿರಸ್ಕರಿಸಿ ಸಮರ್ಥರನ್ನು ಮತದಾನದ ಮೂಲಕ ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಅವಕಾಶವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವು ನೀಡಿದೆ

3. ಕ್ರಿಮಿನಲ್ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆ ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರವೇಶಕ್ಕೆ ತಡೆ ಹಾಕಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಸ್ವಚ್ಛಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆ ದೊರೆತ ಗೊಳ್ಳುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಶುದ್ಧ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯವರು ಶಿಕ್ಷಿತರು ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಸಕ್ರಿಯರಾಗುವಂತೆ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿ ನಿರ್ಮಾಣವಾಗಬೇಕು.

ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳು :-

ನಮ್ಮ ದೇಶವು ಬಹುಪಕ್ಷ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಯ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಗೆ ಇರುವುದನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬಹುದು ಕನಿಷ್ಠ ಮತಗಳನ್ನು ಗಳಿಸಿದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳನ್ನು ನಿಷೇಧಿಸಬೇಕು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಚಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಮಾಡುವ ದುಂದು ವೆಚ್ಚಕ್ಕೆ ಕಡಿವಾಣ ಹಾಕಬೇಕು ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳಿಗೆ ನಿವೃತ್ತಿ ವಯಸ್ಸನ್ನು ಕಡ್ಡಾಯಗೊಳಿಸಬೇಕು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿದವರಿಗೆ ಕನಿಷ್ಠ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಅರ್ಹತೆಯನ್ನು ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಬೇಕು ಜೆ ಎಸ್ ಮಿಲ್ ಹೇಳಿರುವಂತೆ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳಿರುವ ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳಿಗೂ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ

ದೊರಕುವವರಿಗೆ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಯಶಸ್ವಿಯಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಅದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಮತದಾರರು ಅಕ್ಷರಸ್ಥರು ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆ ಉಳ್ಳವರು ಆಗಿದ್ದರೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ನಿಷ್ಪಕ್ಷಪಾತವಾಗಿ ನಡೆಯಲು ಅನುಕೂಲವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ

ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸುಧಾರಣಾ ಸಮಿತಿಗಳು =:-

ಕಾರ್ ಕುಂಡೆ ಅಥವಾ ಜೆಪಿ ಸಮಿತಿ (1975) ಅದರ್ ಮೈಂಡ್ಸ್ ತಾಕುಂಟೆ ಮತ್ತು ಎಮ್ ಆರ್ ಮಹಾಯು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಶಿಫಾರಸ್ಸುಗಳು

1. ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು ಮೂರು ಜನ ಆಯುಕ್ತರನ್ನು ಹೊಂದುವುದು
2. ಮತದಾನಕ್ಕೆ ಕನಿಷ್ಠ 18 ವರ್ಷ ವಯಸ್ಸು ನಿಗದಿ
3. ಮತದಾರರ ಸಮಿತಿ ರಚಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಮುಕ್ತ ಮತ್ತು ನ್ಯಾಯ ಸಮ್ಮತ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನಡೆಸುವುದು

• ಗೋಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಸಮಿತಿ 1990:

1. ಉಪಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಿಗೆ ನಿಗದಿತ ಸಮಯ
 2. ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ರೇವಣಿ ಹಣ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುವುದು
- ಮುಕ್ತ ಮತ್ತು ನ್ಯಾಯ ಸಮ್ಮತ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಮಾರ್ಗಗಳು :
1. ಮುಕ್ತ ಮತ್ತು ನ್ಯಾಯ ಸಮ್ಮತ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಅಗತ್ಯ ಹಾಗೂ ಅಡಿಪಾಯವಾಗಿದೆ ಒಂದಕ್ಕೊಂದು ಆಂತರಿಕ ಸಂಬಂಧವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಆಡಳಿತ ಯಂತ್ರವನ್ನು ಶಕ್ತಿಗೊಳಿಸುವುದಾಗಿದೆ
 2. ಕಾರ್ಯಾಂಗ ಹಾಗೂ ನಮ್ಮ ಸಂಸತ್ತು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗಕ್ಕೆ ಅಗತ್ಯ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯವನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುವುದರ ಮೂಲಕ ಮುಕ್ತ ಮತ್ತು ನ್ಯಾಯಯುತ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನಡೆಸಲು ಸಹಕಾರ ನೀಡಬೇಕು
 3. ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರ ತಡೆಯುವುದರಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಪಕ್ಷವು ಕೆಲವು ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕ ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಶುದ್ಧ ರಾಜಕಾರಣವನ್ನು ನಡೆಸಲು ಮುಂದಾಗಬೇಕು
 4. ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ತೊಡಗಿರುವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯನ್ನು ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಿಂದ ಅನರ್ಹಗೊಳಿಸುವುದು
 5. ಚುನಾವಣಾ ನೀತಿ ಸಂಹಿತೆಯನ್ನು ಕಠಿಣವಾಗಿ ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತರುವುದು ಹಾಗೂ ಯಾರೇ ಆಗಲಿ ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ಉಲ್ಲಂಘಿಸಿದರೆ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಕ್ಕಾನ್ವಯವಾಗಿ ಕ್ರಮ ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳುವಂತಿರಬೇಕು
 6. ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಲಯವು ನೀಡುವ ತೀರ್ಪನ್ನು ಕಡ್ಡಾಯವಾಗಿ ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸುವುದು
 7. ಮತದಾರರಿಗೆ ಮತದಾನದ ಮೌಲ್ಯದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಇನ್ನಷ್ಟು ಅರುಣ್ ಮೂಡಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟತೆಯನ್ನು ಅವರಿಗೆ ಅರ್ಥ ಮಾಡಿಸಬೇಕು
 8. ವಿದ್ಯಾವಂತ ಯುವಕರು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾಲ್ಗೊಳ್ಳುವಂತೆ ಪ್ರೇರಣೆ ನೀಡಬೇಕು ಎಲ್ಲ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹಿಳಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನತೆ ನೀಡಬೇಕು

ಅನವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳನ್ನು ನಿಯಂತ್ರಿಸಬೇಕು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ದುರುದ್ದೇಶದಿಂದ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವವರ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ 1962ರಲ್ಲಿ 492 ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಸ್ಥಾನಕ್ಕೆ ಸಾವಿರದ ಒಂಬತ್ತೊಂದು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಿದ್ದರು. 1977ರಲ್ಲಿ 542 ಸ್ಥಾನಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಎರಡು ಸಾವಿರದ 439 ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಇದ್ದರು ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ೧೯೮೯ರಲ್ಲಿ 542 ಸ್ಥಾನಕ್ಕಾಗಿ 6,160,199 ರಲ್ಲಿ 4,645 ಮತ್ತು 2014ರಲ್ಲಿ 5435 ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿದ್ದರು ಈಗಿರುವ

ಭದ್ರತಾ ರೇವಣಿಯನ್ನು ಇನ್ನೂ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಿ ರೇವಣಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವವರ ಪ್ರಮಾಣವನ್ನು ಇನ್ನೂ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡಬೇಕು ಆಗಿದ್ದಾಗ ಅನಾವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವವರ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ ಕಡಿಮೆಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಪ್ರತಿ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ತಗಲುವ ವೆಚ್ಚವನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿದಾಗ 1952 ರಲ್ಲಿ 10000 45 ಕೋಟಿ ಖರ್ಚಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಕೇವಲ 11.60 ಕೋಟಿ. ಸಾವಿರದ ಒಂಬತ್ತನೂರ ಎಪ್ಪತ್ತೇಳರಲ್ಲಿ 23.3 ಕೋಟಿ.1989ರಲ್ಲಿ 1.50 ಕೋಟಿ. 1977ರಲ್ಲಿ 23.3 ಕೋಟಿ. 1989 ರಲ್ಲಿ 154 ಕೋಟಿ. 1996ರಲ್ಲಿ 597 ಕೋಟಿ. 1999 ರಲ್ಲಿ 880 ಕೋಟಿ. 2004ರಲ್ಲಿ 4500 ಕೋಟಿ ಮತ್ತು 2009ರಲ್ಲಿ 10,000 ಕೋಟಿ ರೂಪಾಯಿ ವೆಚ್ಚವಾಗಿದೆ. ಅನಾವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿ ಖರ್ಚು ಮಾಡುವುದನ್ನು ತಡೆಗಟ್ಟಲು ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದೇ ಬಾರಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನಡೆಸುವ ನಿಯಮವನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತರಬೇಕು.

ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಮತದಾರರ ಪಟ್ಟಿ ಒಂದೇ ರೀತಿಯಾಗಿರಬೇಕು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾನ ಪಟ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅನೇಕ ಮತದಾರರ ಹೆಸರು ತಪ್ಪಿ ಹೋಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾನದ ಪಟ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅನೇಕ ಮತದಾರರ ಹೆಸರು ತಪ್ಪಿ ಹೋಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನಡೆಸುವುದಕ್ಕೆ 15 ದಿನಗಳ ಮೊದಲು ಮತದಾರಿ ಮತದಾನದ ಪಟ್ಟಿಯನ್ನು ಬಿಡುಗಡೆ ಮಾಡಬೇಕು.

* ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಒಂದು ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವುದನ್ನು ತಡೆಗಟ್ಟಬೇಕು ಒಬ್ಬನಿಗೆ ಒಂದೇ ಮತವಿರುವಂತೆ ಒಬ್ಬ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗೆ ಒಂದೇ ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರವಿರಬೇಕು.

*ಪೂರ್ವಭಾವಿ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಫಲಿತಾಂಶವನ್ನು ರದ್ದುಗೊಳಿಸಬೇಕು ಚುನಾವಣೆ ನಡೆಯುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ಮುಂಚೆ ಅನೇಕ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡ ಖಾಸಗಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಸಂಘಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸಮೂಹ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳು ಬಿಡುಗಡೆ ಮಾಡುವ ಪೂರ್ವಭಾವಿ ಫಲಿತಾಂಶವನ್ನು ಆಯೋಗವು ತಡೆಹಿಡಿಯಬೇಕು

* ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ದಾಖಲಾದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಅಕ್ರಮ ಪ್ರಕರಣಗಳನ್ನು ಇತ್ಯರ್ಥ ಪಡಿಸಲು ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡಬೇಕು ಸರ್ಕಾರ ರಚನೆಯಾದ ನಂತರ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಕರಣಗಳನ್ನು ರದ್ದುಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಕಡಿಗೊಳಿಸಬೇಕು

* ಚುನಾವಣಾ ನಡೆಯುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ಮುಂಚಿತವಾಗಿ ಮತದಾರರಿಗೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆ ಮೂಡಿಸಿ ಇದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಸಮೂಹ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ವೇದಿಕೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅರಿವು ಮೂಡಿಸಬೇಕು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಈ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಇದ್ದರೂ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಜಾರಿಯಾಗುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ

* ಮತದಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಇದ್ದಾಗ ಉತ್ತಮ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ರಚನೆಯಾಗಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯ ಜನಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳಾಗಲು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರಬೇಕು ನಿಯಮವನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತರಬೇಕು

* ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕಡ್ಡಾಯವಾಗಿ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾರರ ಪಾತ್ರದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಹೊಸ ಪಠ್ಯಕ್ರಮವನ್ನು ಸೇರಿಸಬೇಕು

* ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು ಖರ್ಚು ಮಾಡುವಂತೆ ವೆಚ್ಚ ಆಯೋಗವು ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಿರುವ ಮಿತಿಯಲ್ಲಿರಬೇಕು ಮತ್ತು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ವೆಚ್ಚದ ಭಾರ್ತಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ನಮೂದಿಸಬೇಕು.

* ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು ನೀಡುವ ಭದ್ರತಾ ರೇವಣಿಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಬೇಕು

* ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲು ಗರಿಷ್ಠ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ನಿಗದಿಪಡಿಸಬೇಕು.

* ಅಮೆರಿಕದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಹಾಗೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕೇಂದ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಿ ತರಬೇತಿ ಪಡೆದ ನಂತರ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲಿಕ್ಕೆ ಅನುಮತಿ ನೀಡಬೇಕು.

* ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗ ನೇಮಿಸಿದ ವೈದ್ಯಕೀಯ ಸಮಿತಿಯಿಂದ ತಪಾಸಣೆ ಮಾಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಮಾನಸಿಕವಾಗಿ ಹಾಗೂ ದೈನಂದಿನ ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ ಕೆಲಸಗಳನ್ನು ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಲು ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯ ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದಾನೆ ಎಂಬ ದೃಢೀಕರಣ ಪಡೆದಿರಬೇಕು ನಂತರವೇ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡಬೇಕು.

* ಮತದಾನದ ಯಂತ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ಯಾವುದೇ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ದುರುಪಯೋಗ ಮಾಡದಂತೆ ಅಕ್ರಮವಾಗಿ ಇದ್ದಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗದಂತೆ ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸಬೇಕು.

* ಎಲೆಕ್ಟ್ರಾನಿಕ್ ಯಂತ್ರಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಮತದಾನ ಮಾಡುವವರಿಗೆ ತಾನು ಚಲಾಯಿಸಿದ ಮತ ಸರಿಯಾಗಿ ದಾಖಲಾಗಿದೆಯೇ ಅಥವಾ ಇಲ್ಲವೇ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಖಾತರಿಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಅನುಕೂಲವಾಗುವಂತೆ ಮತ ಚಲಾಯಿಸಿದ ನಂತರ ಸ್ವೀಕೃತಿ ನೀಡತಕ್ಕದ್ದು ಇದರಿಂದ ಮತಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ತಾಳೆ ಮಾಡಲು ಅನುಕೂಲವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

* ಪರಿಮಳ ಒಳ್ಳೆ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆ ಮತದಾನ ಗುರುತಿಸುವಿಕೆಯು ಬಯೋಮೆಟ್ರಿಕ್ ಪದ್ಧತಿ ಆಗಿರಬೇಕು.

* ಕಾಲಕಾಲಕ್ಕೆ ಸುಸೂತ್ರವಾಗಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯನ್ನು ನಡೆಸಲು ತನ್ನದೇ ಆದ ಸಿಬ್ಬಂದಿ ವರ್ಗವಿರಬೇಕು.

• ಮತ ಎಣಿಕೆ ಮಾಡುವಾಗ ವಾರ್ಡ್ ವಾರ್ಡಿಸದ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ವಾರ್ಡ್ ಗಳ ಮತಗಳನ್ನು ಒಟ್ಟುಗೂಡಿಸಿ ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡಬೇಕು.

• ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಯುವ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸದಿದ್ದರೆ ಅನೇಕ ಅವಘಡಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತರುವುದರ ಮೂಲಕ ಉತ್ತಮ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ತರಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಉಪಸಂಹಾರ :

ರಾಜಕೀಯ ತಜ್ಞರ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯದಂತೆ ಒಂದು ಸರ್ಕಾರ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಅವಿಶ್ವಾಸ ನಿರ್ಣಯ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಅಡಿಲಿದ್ದರೆ ಆಡಳಿತದ ಪಕ್ಷ ಮೇಲೆ ಅಂಕುಶವಿಲ್ಲದೆ ಆಡಳಿತವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಆದರೆ ಪದೇ ಪದೇ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಉರುಳುವುದು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ನಡೆಯುವುದು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಯಶಸ್ಸಿನ ಮಾನದಂಡವಾಗಬಾರದು. ಮತದಾನ ಪವಿತ್ರ ಎಂಬ ಭಾವನೆ ಜನಸಾಮಾನ್ಯರಲ್ಲಿ ಮೂಡಿದಾಗ ಮಾತ್ರ ಮತದಾರರು ಮತಗಟ್ಟೆಗೆ ಹೋಗಿ ಮತ ಚಲಾಯಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ ಆದರೆ ಪದೇಪದೇ ನಡೆಯುವ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಮತದಾರರಿಗೆ ಬೇಸರವನ್ನುಂಟು ಮಾಡುವುದು ಲೋಕಸಭೆ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯಸಭೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಏಕಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳ ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಾ ಆದರೆ ಅದುವೇ ಒಂದು ದೊಡ್ಡ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸುಧಾರಣೆ ಅಂದರೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಪ್ರಾಮಾಣಿಕವಾಗಿ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಿದರೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಯಶಸ್ವಿ ಆಗುತ್ತದೆ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳು ಮತದಾರರು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಅಡಿಗಣ್ಣುಗಳಂತೆ ಇದನ್ನು ಭದ್ರ ಗಳಿಸುವ ಕಾರ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಇಬ್ಬರ ಪಾತ್ರವು ಅಡಗಿದೆ.

ಆಧಾರ ಗ್ರಂಥಗಳು:

ಡಾಕ್ಟರ್ ಆರ್ ಶಂಕುಪ್ಪ, ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು 2011 ಬಿಎಲ್ ಶಂಕರ್

ಡಾಕ್ಟರ್ ಎಚ್ ಎಮ್ ರಾಜಶೇಖರ್ ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮೈಸೂರು 2013

ಅಗ್ರವಾನ್ ಶಾಮ್ ಸುಂದರ್ 1998 ರಿಲಿಜನ್ ಮತ್ತು ಕ್ಯಾಸ್ಪ್ ಪಾಲಿಟಿಕ್ಸ್ ಜೈಪುರ ರಾವತ್

ಎಲೆಕ್ಷನ್ ಕಮಿಷನ್ ಆಫ್ ಇಂಡಿಯಾ 2004 ಪ್ರೊಪೋಸ್ಡ್ ಎಲೆಕ್ಷನ್ ಕಲ್ ರಿಫಾರ್ಮ್ಸ್ ನ್ಯೂ ಡೆಲ್ಲಿ

ಪುಂಡಲಿಕರ್ ವಿಎ ಪೈ ಮತ್ತು ಕಶ್ಯಪ್ ಸುಭಾಷ್ ಸಿ 201 ಪ್ರೊಲಿಟಿಕ್ಲ್ ರಿಫಾರ್ಮ್ಸ್ ಅರಿಸ್ಸಿಂಗ್ ಸಿವಿಕ್ ಸಾವಿರ ಅಂಟಿ ನ್ಯೂ ದೆಹಲಿಪಬ್ಲಿಷೆಸ್

ಗಣೇಶನ್ ಕೆ 1994 ಎಲೆಕ್ಷನ್ ರಿಫಾರ್ಮ್ಸ್ ಪಾರ್ಲಿಮೆಂಟ್ಸ್ ಅಫೇರ್ಸ್

ಬಿ ವೆಂಕಟೇಶ್ ಕುಮಾರ್ 2002 ಕ್ರಿಟಿಕ್ಲ್ ಇಶ್ಯೂಸ್ ಇನ್ ಎಲೆಕ್ಷನ್ ರಿಫಾರ್ಮ್ಸ್ ಪಬ್ಲಿಶ್ಡ್ ಬೈ ಇಂಡಿಯನ್ ಪ್ರೊಲಿಟಿಕ್ಲ್ ಸೈನ್ಸ್ ಅಸೋಸಿಯೇಷನ್.

2019ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ವಿವಾದಾಂಶಗಳು**Yogesha H S***Research Scholar, University Mysore***Dr. Krishan Hombal***Professor, University of Mysore***ಸಾರಲೇಖ:**

ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ (Citizenship Amendment Act - CAA) 2019, ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರವು 1955ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯನ್ನು ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಮಾಡಿದ್ದು, ಪಾಕಿಸ್ತಾನ, ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ಅಫ್ಘಾನಿಸ್ತಾನದಿಂದ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಹಿಂಸೆಗೆ ಒಳಗಾದ ಹಿಂದೂ, ಸಿಖ್, ಬೌದ್ಧ, ಜೈನ, ಪಾರ್ಸಿ ಮತ್ತು ಕ್ರಿಶ್ಚಿಯನ್ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳ ಧರ್ಮೀಯರಿಗೆ ಭಾರತೀಯ ಪೌರತ್ವವನ್ನು ನೀಡಲು ಉದ್ದೇಶಿಸಿದೆ. ಈ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು 2014ರ ಡಿಸೆಂಬರ್ 31ರೊಳಗೆ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ಬಂದಿರುವವರನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ, ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಮುಸಲ್ಮಾನರು ಸಮುದಾಯದವರನ್ನು ಹೊರತುಪಡಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದು, ಇದು ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಧರ್ಮನಿರಪೇಕ್ಷತೆಯ ತತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂಬ ಟೀಕೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಗುರಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. ವಿಮರ್ಶಕರು ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯನ್ನು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಪೌರತ್ವ ನೋಂದಣಿ (NRC) ಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧ ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಿ, ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ ಸಮುದಾಯದವರನ್ನು ಹೊರತುಪಡಿಸುವ ಭಯವನ್ನು ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ದೇಶಾದ್ಯಂತ ಪ್ರತಿಭಟನೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಪ್ರೇರಣೆಯಾಯಿತು. ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ ಸಂಗತಿ ಎಂದರೆ ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಬದ್ಧತೆಯನ್ನು ಸರ್ವೋಚ್ಚ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಲಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಶ್ನಿಸಿ, ಅನೇಕರು ಅರ್ಜಿ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ ಪ್ರಕರಣಗಳು ನ್ಯಾಯಾಲಯದ ಅಂಗಳದಲ್ಲಿವೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಸಂಶೋಧನಾ ಲೇಖನದಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಧನಾತ್ಮಕ ಮತ್ತು ಋಣಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಂಶಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿರಣೆ ಬೀರಲು 2019ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಭಾರತದ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಧರ್ಮ ನಿರಪೇಕ್ಷ ತತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ತದ್ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾದುದಾಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಅದನ್ನು ಅಮಲಾಗುವಾಗಿ ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಿ, ಮರು ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಗೊಳಪಡಿಸಿ, ಒಳಗೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆಯ ಭಾರತದ ತತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಅನುರೂಪ ವಾಗುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡುವುದು ಕಾಲಮಾನದ ಅಗತ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ವಾದಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಪೀಠಿಕೆ

ಭಾರತದ ಸಮಕಾಲೀನ ರಾಜಕಾರಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಚರ್ಚಿತ ಚರ್ವಣಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿರುವ ಅಸಂಖ್ಯಾತ ವಿವಾದಾಂಶಗಳಿವೆ. ಈ ವಿವಾದಾಂಶಗಳು ಭಾರತದ ಬೃಹತ್ ಗಾತ್ರದ ಉದಾರವಾದಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧಿಕ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ಒಳಗಿನಿಂದ ಮತ್ತು ಹೊರಗಿನಿಂದ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರ ಗಮನ ಸೆಳೆಯುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಅಂತಹ ಜ್ವಲಂತ ವಿವಾದಾಂಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ 2019ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಒಂದು. ಸಾರ್ವಭೌಮ ಸಮಾಜವಾದಿ ಜಾತ್ಯತೀತ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಗಣರಾಜ್ಯವಾದ ಭಾರತ ಬಹುದರ್ಮಿಯ ,ಬಹು ಜನಾಂಗೀಯ ಬಹುಭಾಷಿಕರ ಪೌರರನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾಗಿದೆ. ಭಾರತ ಅನೇಕರಿಗೆ ಆಶ್ರಯದಾಣವಾಗಿದೆ. ಭಾರತದ ನೆರೆಹೊರೆ ದೇಶಗಳಾದ ಅಫ್ಘಾನಿಸ್ತಾನ ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶ ಭೂತಾನ್ ಮಾಲ್ಡೀವ್ಸ್ ನೇಪಾಳ ಪಾಕಿಸ್ತಾನ ಶ್ರೀಲಂಕಾದಂತಹ ನೆರೆಹೊರೆಯ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳಿಂದ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ವಲಸಿಗರು ಬಂದು ನೆಲೆಸಿದ್ದುಂಟು. ತತ್ಪರಿಣಾಮವಾಗಿ ಭಾರತದ ಜನಸಂಖ್ಯಾ ರಚನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿದೇಶದಿಂದ ಬಂದ ವಲಸಿಗರು ಸೇರಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಇದು ದೇಶದ ಜನರ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಅಧಿಕಾರದ ಸಂರಚನೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳನ್ನುಂಟು ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದೆ. 1950ರಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾರಿಗೊಂಡ ಭಾರತದ ಘನ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ದ್ವಿತೀಯ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಪೌರತ್ವದ ಕುರಿತಾದ ವಿಧಿ ವಿಧಾನಗಳಿವೆ. ಆ ವಿಧಿ ವಿಧಾನಗಳ

ಚೌಕಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತದ ಸಂಸತ್ತು ಕಾಲ ಕಾಲಕ್ಕೆ ರೂಪಿಸಿದ ಪೌರತ್ವ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಗಳು ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಗೊಂಡಿವೆ. ಅವುಗಳ ಸಾಲಿನಲ್ಲಿ 2019ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ತೀರಾ ಇತ್ತೀಚಿನದಾಗಿದೆ. ಬದಲಾದ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಅಂತರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯಿಂದ ಉಂಟಾಗಬಹುದಾದ ಲಾಭ ಹಾನಿಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ವ್ಯಾಪಕ ಚರ್ಚೆಯಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಈ ಚರ್ಚೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರನ್ನು ಪರ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಗುಂಪುಗಳನ್ನಾಗಿ ವಿಭಜಿಸಿದೆ. ಈ ಪರ ವಿರೋಧ ಚರ್ಚೆಯನ್ನು ಬರೀ ರಾಜನೀತಿಕ ಚೌಕಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ನೋಡಿದರೆ ಸಾಲದು ಭಾರತದ ಭೌಗೋಳಿಕ ರಾಜಕೀಯದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಅದರ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಮಾಜ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರೀಯತೆ ,ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಆರ್ಥಿಕತೆ ,ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಏಕತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅನೇಕತೆಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡ ಸಮಸ್ತ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನೇ ಗಮನದಲ್ಲಿಟ್ಟುಕೊಂಡು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಿ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸುವ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆ ಇದೆ. ಈ ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವಿಧಾಯಾಮಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ವಿವಿಧ ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳನ್ನು 2019ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಸಹಜವಾಗಿಯೇ ಗಮನಹಾಕರ್ಪಕ ಸಂಗತಿಯಾಗಿದೆ.

2019ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಪರಿಚಯ.

ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧ ಸಮಾಜಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಜ್ಞ ಬ್ರಯಾನ್ ಎಸ್. ಟರ್ನರ್ ಅವರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ “ ಪೌರತ್ವ ಕೇವಲ ರಾಜ್ಯವು ನೀಡುವ ಕಾನೂನಾತ್ಮಕ ಸ್ಥಾನಮಾನವಲ್ಲ, ಬದಲಾಗಿ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳು, ಕರ್ತವ್ಯಗಳು, ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಮುದಾಯದೊಳಗಿನ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುವ ಒಂದು ಬಹು ಆಯಾಮದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದು ರಾಜ್ಯದೊಂದಿಗೆ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯ ಔಪಚಾರಿಕ ಸಂಬಂಧ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಾಜದ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ನಾಗರಿಕ ರಚನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅವರ ಅನೌಪಚಾರಿಕ ಏಕೀಕರಣವನ್ನು ಸೂಚಿಸುತ್ತದೆ” ಎಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ.(1)

ಪೌರತ್ವ ಎಂಬ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ ಯಾವುದೇ ಒಂದು ಸಾರ್ವಭೌಮ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಕಾನೂನಿನ ಸದಸ್ಯತ್ವವಾಗಿದೆ ಅಥವಾ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿದ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಎಂದು ಕಾನೂನಿನಡಿ ಗುರುತಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಯಾಗಿದೆ ಎನ್ನಬಹುದು. ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ಪ್ರತಿಯಾಗಿ ಪೌರರಿಗೆ ಕೆಲವು ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳು ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಪೌರತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಏಕ ಪೌರತ್ವ ದ್ವಿಪೌರತ್ವ ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಪೌರತ್ವ ಮತ್ತು ಜಾಗತಿಕ ಪೌರತ್ವ ಎಂಬ ಅನೇಕ ಪ್ರಕಾರಗಳಿವೆ. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪೌರತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಭಾಗ ಎರಡರಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಧಿ 5 ರಿಂದ 11 ರವರೆಗೆ ಚರ್ಚಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ(2). ಭಾರತದ ಸಂಸತ್ತು ಆರಂಭದಲ್ಲಿ ದೇಶದ ಎಲ್ಲ ನಿವಾಸಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಪೌರತ್ವವನ್ನು ನೀಡುವ ಉದ್ದೇಶಕ್ಕಾಗಿ 1955ರಲ್ಲಿ ಪೌರತ್ವ ಕಾಯಿದೆಯನ್ನು ಅಂಗೀಕರಿಸಿತು. ಮುಂದುವರಿದು ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪೌರತ್ವವನ್ನು ಯಾರಿಗೆ ನೀಡಬೇಕು ಎಂಬುದಕ್ಕೆ ಪೂರಕವಾಗಿ 1955 ರ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಜನಿಸಿದವರಿಗೆ, ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಂಜಾತರಿಗೆ, ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರದಿಂದ ಗುರುತಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟ ಯಾವುದಾದರೂ ಯೋಜನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ವಲಸೆ ಬಂದವರಿಗೆ ಅಥವಾ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ಯಾವುದೇ ಭೂ ಪ್ರದೇಶ ಸೇರ್ಪಡೆಯಾದಾಗ ಅಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಭಾರತದ ಪೌರತ್ವ ನೀಡುವುದಾಗಿ ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸಲಾಯಿತು.(3)

ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ 2019 ಅನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತರಲು ಮಾರ್ಚ್ 11,2019 ರಂದು ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಕೆಲವು ನಿಯಮಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಕಟಿಸಿತು. ಅದರಂತೆ ಡಿಸೆಂಬರ್ 31, 2014 ರ ಮೊದಲು ಭಾರತವನ್ನು ಪ್ರವೇಶಿಸಿದ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ ಬಹುಸಂಖ್ಯಾತ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳಾದ ಪಾಕಿಸ್ತಾನ, ಅಫಘಾನಿಸ್ತಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶದಿಂದ ಹಿಂದೂ, ಕ್ರಿಶ್ಚಿಯನ್, ಬೌದ್ಧ, ಜೈನ್, ಸಿಖ್ ಮತ್ತು ಪಾರ್ಸಿ ವಲಸಿಗರಿಗೆ ಈ ಕಾಯಿದೆಯು ಭಾರತೀಯ ಪೌರತ್ವದ ಅರ್ಹತೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಡಿಸೆಂಬರ್ 11, 2019 ರಂದು ಸಂಸತ್ತಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಅಂಗೀಕಾರಗೊಂಡು ಡಿಸೆಂಬರ್ 12,2019 ರಂದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಪತಿ ಒಪ್ಪಿಗೆ ಪಡೆದು ಅಧಿಕೃತವಾಗಿ ಜಾರಿಗೊಂಡ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಅಪಘಾನಿಸ್ತಾನ ,ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶ ,ಪಾಕಿಸ್ತಾನ ಈ ದೇಶಗಳಿಂದ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಹಿಂಸೆಯ ಕಾರಣದಿಂದ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ಬಂದು

ಆಶ್ರಯ ಪಡೆಯುವ ನಿರಾಶ್ರಿತರಿಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ಕಲ್ಪಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದು ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಹಿಂದೂ ಸಿಖ್ ಬೌದ್ಧ ಜೈನ ಪಾರ್ಸಿ ಮತ್ತು ಕ್ರಿಶ್ಚಿಯನ್ ಧರ್ಮೀಯರಿಗೆ ಪೌರತ್ವ ನೀಡಲು ಸೌಲಭ್ಯ ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಏನೇನು ಬದಲಾವಣೆ

2019ರಲ್ಲಿ ಕೈಗೊಂಡ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಯ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ನೆರೆಯ ಆಫ್ಫಾನಿಸ್ತಾನ ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶ ಪಾಕಿಸ್ತಾನದಿಂದ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ವಲಸೆ ಬಂದವರಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಸಮುದಾಯ(ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರು) ಗಳಿಗೆ ಸೇರಿದವರಿಗೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಭಾರತದ ಪೌರತ್ವ ನೀಡಬೇಕು ಎಂಬ ಅಂಶವನ್ನು ಸೇರಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ ಈ ಧರ್ಮೀಯರು ತಮ್ಮ ದೇಶದಿಂದ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾಲಿಟ್ಟ ದಿನಾಂಕದಿಂದಲೇ ಅವರಿಗೆ ಭಾರತದ ಪೌರತ್ವ ಅನ್ವಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಆ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳ ಸದಸ್ಯರ ಭಾರತೀಯ ವಾಸ್ತವ್ಯವನ್ನು ಕಾನೂನುಬಾಹಿರ ಎಂದು ಪರಿಗಣಿಸದೆ, ಅವರ ಮೇಲೆ ದಾಖಲಾಗಿರುವ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಕಾನೂನಾತ್ಮಕ ಪ್ರಕರಣಗಳಿಂದ ಅವರಿಗೆ ಪೌರತ್ವ ಸಿಕ್ಕಿದ ಕೂಡಲೇ ಮುಕ್ತಿಗೊಳಿಸಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. (4)

2019ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳು:

ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಗೆ ಅದರದೇ ಆದ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳಿವೆ. ಅಪಘಾನಿಸ್ತಾನ, ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ಪಾಕಿಸ್ತಾನದ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂಮೇತರ ಧರ್ಮೀಯರಾದ ಹಿಂದೂ, ಸಿಖ್, ಬೌದ್ಧ, ಜೈನ, ಪಾರ್ಸಿ ಮತ್ತು ಕ್ರಿಶ್ಚಿಯನ್ ಧರ್ಮೀಯರಿಗೆ, ಭಾರತೀಯ ಪೌರತ್ವ ನೀಡುವುದು ಇದರ ಗಣ ಉದ್ದೇಶವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದರ ಇತರ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳು ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನಂತಿವೆ:- (5)

*ಪೌರತ್ವ ಪಡೆಯುವ ಅವಧಿ ಕಡಿಗೊಳಿಸುವುದು:

ಈ ಮುಂಚಿನ ಪೌರತ್ವ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ಪಡೆಯಲು 11 ವರ್ಷಗಳ ವಾಸದ ಅವಧಿ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿತ್ತು. ಈ 2019ರ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯಡಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ನಿರಾಶ್ರಿತರಿಗೆ ಐದು ವರ್ಷದಲ್ಲಿ ಪೌರತ್ವ ಪಡೆಯಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.

*ಅಕ್ರಮ ವಲಸೆಯನ್ನು ನಿಯಂತ್ರಿಸುವುದು:

ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಕ್ರಮ ವಲಸಿಗೆ ಕಡಿವಾಣ ಹಾಕುವುದು. ವಿವಿಧ ಮೂಲಗಳ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಕ್ರಮವಾಗಿ ವಾಸಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವ ವಿದೇಶಿ ನಾಗರಿಕರ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ 20 ಮಿಲಿಯನ್ ಅಧವಾ ಅದಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಇದೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಅಕ್ರಮ ವಲಸಿಗರನ್ನು ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿ ಅಡಿ ಪರಿಗಣಿಸದೆ, ಅಪಘಾನಿಸ್ತಾನ, ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶ, ಪಾಕಿಸ್ತಾನ ಈ ಈ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಶೋಷಣೆಗೆ ಒಳಗಾದ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂಮೇತರ ಧರ್ಮೀಯರಿಗೆ ಪೌರತ್ವ ನೀಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ದೇಶದ ಆಂತರಿಕ ಸುರಕ್ಷತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸೌಹಾರ್ದತೆ ಕಾಯ್ದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. (6)

*ಮಾನವೀಯ ನೆಲೆಗಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಸಹಾಯ ನೀಡುವುದು:

ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಶೋಷಣೆಗೆ ಒಳಗಾದ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಮಾನವೀಯ ನೆರವು ಒದಗಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ದೇಶದ ಸಹಾನುಭೂತಿಯ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನವನ್ನು ಬಲಪಡಿಸುವ ಉದ್ದೇಶವು ಇದಕ್ಕಿದೆ.

• ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಸಮಾನತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಹಿಷ್ಣುತೆಯನ್ನು ವರ್ಧಿಸುವುದು:

ನೆರೆಹೊರೆಯ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರು ದೌರ್ಜನ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಒಳಗಾಗಿ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ವಲಸೆ ಬಂದಾಗ ಅವರಿಗೆ ಪೌರತ್ವವನ್ನು ನೀಡುವುದರಿಂದ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಸಹ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಸಮಾನತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಹಿಷ್ಣುತೆ ವೃದ್ಧಿಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

*ಈಶಾನ್ಯ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಜನರಭಾವನೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಗೌರವಿಸುವುದು:

ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಈಶಾನ್ಯ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಾದ ಅರುಣಾಚಲ ಪ್ರದೇಶ, ಅಸ್ಸಾಂ, ಮಣಿಪುರ, ಮೇಘಾಲಯ, ಮಿಝೋರಾಂ, ನಾಗಾಲಾಂಡ್ ಮತ್ತು ಸಿಕ್ಕಿಂನ ಕೆಲವು ವಿಶೇಷ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಿಗೆ ಅನ್ವಯಿಸುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಕಾರಣ ಈ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳು ತನ್ನದೇ ಆದ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಅವರ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಹಾಗೂ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ವೈವಿಧ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಗೌರವಿಸುವ ಉದ್ದೇಶವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ.

ಅಂತರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳನ್ನು ಸುಧಾರಿಸುವುದು:

ನೆರೆಹೊರೆಯ ದೇಶಗಳಿಂದ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ಬಂದ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರಿಗೆ ಪೌರತ್ವ ನೀಡುವುದರ ಮೂಲಕ ಭಾರತವು ಅಂತರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಬಂಧ ಸುಧಾರಿಸುವ ಉದ್ದೇಶವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ.

ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಭದ್ರತೆಯನ್ನು ಬಲಪಡಿಸುವುದು:

ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಅಕ್ರಮ ವಲಸೆ ನಿಯಂತ್ರಣ ಮಾಡುವುದರ ಮೂಲಕ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದ ಆಂತರಿಕ ಭದ್ರತೆಯನ್ನು ಬಲಪಡಿಸುವ ಮಹದ್ದೇಶವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ.

ಒಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇಳುವುದಾದರೆ ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಈ ಮೇಲೆ ತಿಳಿಸಿದ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನ ಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಮಹದ್ದೇಶವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ.

2019ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಪರಿವಾದ ನಿಲುವುಗಳು:-

2019ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳು ಏನೇ ಇರಲಿ, ಭಾರತದ ಉದ್ದಗಲಕ್ಕೂ ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಕೆಲವರು ದೃಷ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ವರವಾದರೆ ಮತ್ತೆ ಕೆಲವರಿಗೆ ನುಂಗಲಾರದ ತುತ್ತಾಗಿದೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದಲೇ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಪ್ರದತ್ತವಾದ ವಾಕ್ ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯವನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ ಉಪಯೋಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡ ಭಾರತೀಯರಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲವರು 2019ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಪರಿವಾಗಿ ತಮ್ಮ ವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ಮಂಡಿಸಿದ್ದುಂಟು. ಅಂತಹ ವಾದಗಳನ್ನು ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.

ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ನಿಲುವು:

ಭಾರತೀಯ ಜನತಾ ಪಕ್ಷ ನೇತೃತ್ವದ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ಮೈತ್ರಿಕೂಟದ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರವು 2019 ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯನ್ನು ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಗೊಳಿಸಿದೆ. ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಪಾಕಿಸ್ತಾನ, ಅಫಘಾನಿಸ್ತಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶಗಳು ಇಸ್ಲಾಮಿಕ್ ಗಣರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಾಗಿವೆ, ಅಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಮರು ಬಹುಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಅವರನ್ನು ಕಿರುಕುಳಕ್ಕೊಳಗಾದ ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರು ಎಂದು ಪರಿಗಣಿಸಲಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸಿದೆ.

ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಪ್ರಕಾರ, ಈ ಮಸೂದೆಯು ಯಾರೊಬ್ಬರ ಪೌರತ್ವವನ್ನು ಕಸಿದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಬದಲಿಗೆ ಪೌರತ್ವವನ್ನು ನೀಡುವ ಗುರಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ.

ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಮುಸಲ್ಮಾನ ಸಮುದಾಯವನ್ನು ಹೊರತುಪಡಿಸಿ, ಬೇರೆ ಯಾವುದೇ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಅರ್ಜಿಯನ್ನು ಈ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಮಸೂದೆಯ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ಭರವಸೆ ನೀಡಿದೆ.

ಸಿ. ಎ. ಎ ಧರ್ಮದ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಪೌರತ್ವವನ್ನು ನೀಡುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಕಿರುಕುಳ ಕೊಳಗಾದ ಸಂತ್ರಸ್ತತೆಯ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಪೌರತ್ವ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದಕಾರಣ ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಉಲ್ಲಂಘನೆಯ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆ ಇಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ 'ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಕಿರುಕುಳಕ್ಕೊಳಗಾದ' ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ವಲಸೆಬಂದ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಮೇತರರಿಗೆ ಪೌರತ್ವ ನೀಡಲಾಗುವುದು ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಿಲ್ಲ. ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾಕಿಸ್ತಾನ, ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ಅಫಘಾನಿಸ್ತಾನದಿಂದ ಬಂದ ಹಿಂದೂ, ಬೌದ್ಧ, ಜೈನ, ಪಾರ್ಸಿ, ಸಿಖ್ ಮತ್ತು ಕ್ರೈಸ್ತ ಸಮುದಾಯದವರಿಗೆ ಆದ್ಯತೆಯ ಮೇಲೆ ಪೌರತ್ವ ನೀಡಲಾಗುವುದು ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಿದೆ.

ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ 2019ರ ಪರಿವಾಗಿ ನಮ್ಮ ಭಾರತದ ಪ್ರಧಾನ ಮಂತ್ರಿಗಳಾದ ಶ್ರೀ ನರೇಂದ್ರ ಮೋದಿ ಅವರು ತಮ್ಮ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯ ಸಹ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸಿ. "ವಿಪುಲ ಮತ್ತು ವ್ಯಾಪಕವಾದ ಚರ್ಚೆಯ ನಂತರ ಲೋಕಸಭೆ 2019 ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ (ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ) ಮಸೂದೆಯನ್ನು ಅಂಗೀಕರಿಸಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಖುಷಿಪಟ್ಟಿದ್ದೇನೆ" ಮತ್ತು "ಮಸೂದೆ ಭಾರತದ ಶತಮಾನಗಳ ಹಳೆಯ ಒಗ್ಗೂಡಿಸುವಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಮಾನವೀಯ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿದೆ" ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಿದ್ದಾರೆ.(6)

ಭಾರತದ ವಿದೇಶಾಂಗ ಸಚಿವರಾದ ಎಸ್. ಜೈಶಂಕರ್ ಅವರು ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ, 2019 ರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ತಮ್ಮ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯವನ್ನು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸುತ್ತಾ “ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಮಾನವೀಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ಪಾಕಿಸ್ತಾನ, ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ಅಫ್ಘಾನಿಸ್ತಾನದ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕಲ್ಪ ಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರ ಮೇಲೆ 1947 ಪರಿಣಾಮದಿಂದ ಉಂಟಾದ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಬಿಜೆಪಿಯ ಹಿರಿಯ ನಾಯಕ ಸುಬ್ರಹ್ಮಣ್ಯ ಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಮಾತನಾಡುತ್ತ, ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ (CAA) ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳಿಗೆ ರಕ್ಷಣೆ ಪ್ರಾಪ್ತವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಮುಂದುವರಿದು ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಭಾರತೀಯ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಮರನ್ನು ಪ್ರಭಾವಿತಗೊಳಿಸುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ಸಮರ್ಥಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಈ ರೀತಿಯಾಗಿ ಭಾರತದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನಾಯಕರು ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ 2019 ರ ಕುರಿತು ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮರ್ಥಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ . ಅದೇನೇ ಇರಲಿ ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯನ್ನು ಕೇವಲ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನದಿಂದ ಮಾತ್ರವೇ ಪರಿಗಣಿಸದೆ ಅದರ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ ದೇಶದ ಕಾನೂನು ಚೌಕಟ್ಟು, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಬಹು ಆಯಾಮಿಯ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಯಿಂದ ಪರಿವೀಕ್ಷಿಸಿ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗೆ ಒಳಪಡಿಸು ದುದೇ ಆದರೆ ಇದೊಂದು ಉತ್ತಮ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯಾಗಿ ರೂಪುಗೊಳ್ಳುವ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಗುಣಲಕ್ಷಣಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ.

2019ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾದ ವಾದಗಳು :-

2019ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ರಾಜಧಾನಿ ಪ್ರದೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ಈಶಾನ್ಯ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳು ಸೇರಿದಂತೆ ದೇಶಾದ್ಯಂತ ವ್ಯಾಪಕ ಪ್ರತಿಭಟನೆಗಳು ನಡೆದಿವೆ. ಈ ಕ್ರಮವು ತಮ್ಮ "ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳು, ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಭೂಮಿಯ ಹಕ್ಕು"ಗಳಿಗೆ ನಷ್ಟವನ್ನು ಉಂಟುಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಮತ್ತು ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶದಿಂದ ಮತ್ತಷ್ಟು ವಲಸೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರೇರೇಪಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬ ಭಯದಿಂದ ಅಸ್ಸಾಂ ಮತ್ತು ಇತರ ಈಶಾನ್ಯ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿನ ಪ್ರತಿಭಟನೆಯು ಹಿಂಸಾತ್ಮಕವಾಗಿ ತಿರುಗಿತು. ಪೌರತ್ವ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯಲ್ಲಿನ ಹೊಸ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಯು ಮುಸ್ಲಿಮರ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ತಾರತಮ್ಯವನ್ನುಂಟುಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ದೇಶದ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸಿರುವ ಸಮಾನತೆಯ ಹಕ್ಕನ್ನು ಉಲ್ಲಂಘಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬ ಆತಂಕವನ್ನು ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.

2019ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ವಿರೋಧವಾಗಿ ಅನೇಕ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಚರ್ಚಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ಈ ಕೆಳಕಂಡಂತೆ ನೋಡಬಹುದು.

1. ಇದು ನಮ್ಮ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ 14ನೇ ವಿಧಿಯ ಸಮಾನತೆ ತತ್ವದ ಉಲ್ಲಂಘನೆಯಾಗಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಪೀಠಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸಲಾದ ಜಾತ್ಯತೀತತೆಯ ತತ್ವದ ಉಲ್ಲಂಘನೆಯಾಗಿದೆ.
3. ಭಾರತವು ಶ್ರೀಲಂಕಾದಿಂದ ಬಂದ ತಮಿಳರು ಹಾಗೂ ಮಯನ್ಮಾರ್ ನಿಂದ ಬಂದ ಹಿಂದೂ ಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುವ ಹಲವಾರು ನಿರಾಶ್ರಿತರನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ ಆದರೆ ಅವರು ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿಗೆ ಒಳಪಡುವುದಿಲ್ಲ.
4. ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಸರ್ಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಅಕ್ರಮ ವಲಸಿಗರು ಮತ್ತು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಕಿರುಕುಳ ಕೊಳಗದವರ ನಡುವೆ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸವನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಕಷ್ಟಕರ ವಾದುದಾಗಿದೆ.
5. ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಪಾಕಿಸ್ತಾನ, ಅಫಘಾನಿಸ್ತಾನ ಈ ಮೂರು ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಿರುವ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ದಬ್ಬಾಳಿಕೆಗಳ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಬೆಳಕು ಚೆಲ್ಲುತ್ತದೆ ಹೀಗಾಗಿ ಈ ಈ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳೊಡನೆ ನಮ್ಮ ದ್ವಿಪಕ್ಷೀಯ ಸಂಬಂಧವನ್ನು ಹದಗೆಡಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.
6. ಈ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಇತರ ಶೋಷಿತ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ತನ್ನ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿಯಿಂದ ಹೊರಗಿಟ್ಟಿದೆ. ಭಾರತದ ನೆರೆಹೊರೆಯ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಮೇತರ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳಾದ, ಶ್ರೀಲಂಕಾದಿಂದ ಹಿಂದೂ

ಸಮುದಾಯದ ನಿರಾಶ್ರಿತರು ಟಿಬೆಟ್‌ನಿಂದ ಬೌದ್ಧ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ನಿರಾಶ್ರಿತರು ಶೋಷಣೆಯ ಕಾರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ವಲಸೆ ಬಂದಿದ್ದರೂ ಇವರಿಗೆ ಪೌರತ್ವ ನೀಡುವುದನ್ನು ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿಲ್ಲ.

7. ಮಯನ್ಮಾರ್ ದೇಶದಿಂದ ಬಂದಿರುವ ರೋಹಿಂಗ್ಯಾ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ ನಿರಾಶ್ರಿತರನ್ನು ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿಯು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿಲ್ಲ. ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಅವರನ್ನು ಮಯನ್ಮಾರ್ ಗೆ ಗಡಿಪಾರು ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದೆ.

8. ಈ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿಯಿಂದ ಕಿರುಕುಳಕ್ಕೊಳಗಾದ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಮರನ್ನು ಹೊರಗಡೆಹುವುದು ಪಾಕಿಸ್ತಾನ ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ಆಫ್ಘಾನಿಸ್ತಾನದ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಮರಿಗೆ ಈ ಹೊಸ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಅಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪೌರತ್ವಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ತ್ವರಿತ ಅರ್ಹತೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಿಲ್ಲ. ಇದನ್ನು ವಿಮರ್ಶಕರು ಇಸ್ಲಾಮಿಕ್ ವಿರೋಧಿ ಭಾವನೆಯ ಕಾರಣದಿಂದ ಹೊರಗಿಡಲಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಪ್ರಶ್ನಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

3. ಈ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ದೇಶದ ಈಶಾನ್ಯ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಅಭ್ಯಂತರ ಇರುವುದನ್ನು ಕಾಣುತ್ತೇವೆ. ಅಸ್ಸಾಂ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತರ ಪೂರ್ವ ಭಾಗಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜನರು ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಗೆ ಅಪಾಯವನ್ನು ಉಂಟು ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ಭಯಪಟ್ಟಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅಕ್ರಮ ವಲಸೆಯಿಂದ ಜನಸಾಂಖ್ಯಿಕ ಸಮತೋಲನ ಬದಲಾಗುವ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸಂಪತ್ತು ಹಾನಿಯಾಗುವ ಸಾಧ್ಯತೆಗಳಿವೆ.

5. ಈ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ವಿಭಜನೆ ಉಂಟು ಮಾಡುವ ಸಾಧ್ಯತೆ ಇದೆ. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಅನ್ವಯಿಸುವುದರಿಂದ ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ದ್ವೇಷ ಮತ್ತು ಅಸಮಾನತೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬ ಆತಂಕ ವ್ಯಕ್ತವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಈ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಈ ರೀತಿ ವಿರೋಧಾ ಅಂಶಗಳ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಕೆಲವು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಗಣ್ಯರು ಚಿಂತಕರು ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಅವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ನಾಯಕ ಮಲ್ಲಿಕಾರ್ಜುನ ಖರ್ಗೆ ಅವರು ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ (CAA) 2019 ವಿರುದ್ಧ ತಮ್ಮ ಆಕ್ಷೇಪಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಅವರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ, ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಭಾರತದ ಸಾಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ ಧರ್ಮನಿರಪೇಕ್ಷತೆಯ ತತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದರಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ ಸಮುದಾಯವನ್ನು ಹೊರತುಪಡಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 14 (ಸಮಾನತೆಗೆ ಹಕ್ಕು) ಉಲ್ಲಂಘನೆಯಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಅವರು ಆರೋಪಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಈ ವಿವಾದಿತ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಕುರಿತು ದೇಶದ ಮತ್ತೊಬ್ಬ ಮಹಿಳಾ ನಾಯಕಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಪಶ್ಚಿಮ ಬಂಗಾಳದ ಮುಖ್ಯಮಂತ್ರಿ ಮತ್ತು ತೃಣಮೂಲ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ (ಟಿಎಂಸಿ) ನಾಯಕಿ ಮಮತಾ ಬ್ಯಾನರ್ಜಿ ಅವರು 2019 ರ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯನ್ನು (ಸಿಎಎ) ಸತತವಾಗಿ ವಿರೋಧಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅವರು ಇದನ್ನು ತಾರತಮ್ಯವೆಂದು ಪರಿಗಣಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಇದು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವ್ಯಾಪಿ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ನಾಗರಿಕರ ನೋಂದಣಿಯ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಬಹುದು ಎಂದು ಅವರು ಕಳವಳ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇದು ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳನ್ನು ಉಲ್ಲಂಘಿಸಬಹುದು ಮತ್ತು ದುರ್ಬಲ ಗುಂಪುಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊರತುಪಡಿಸಬಹುದು ಎಂಬ ಆತಂಕ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇನ್ನು ಈ ವಿವಾದಿತ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅಂತರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ, ವಿಶ್ವಸಂಸ್ಥೆಯ ಮಾನವ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳ ಹೈ ಕಮಿಷನರ್ ಕಚೇರಿಯು ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯನ್ನು ಟೀಕಿಸಿದೆ. ಮತ್ತು ಇದನ್ನು "ಮೂಲಭೂತವಾಗಿ ತಾರತಮ್ಯ ಸ್ವಭಾವ" ಎಂದು ಕರೆದಿದೆ. "ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಶಾಲವಾದ ನೈಸರ್ಗಿಕೀಕರಣ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳು ಜಾರಿಯಲ್ಲಿದ್ದರೂ, ಈ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಗಳು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯತೆಗೆ ಜನರ ಪ್ರವೇಶದ ಮೇಲೆ ತಾರತಮ್ಯದ ಪರಿಣಾಮವನ್ನು ಬೀರುತ್ತವೆ" ಎಂದು ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸಿದೆ.

ನಾಗರಿಕತೆ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ (CAA) 2019 ಕುರಿತು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ತೀರ್ಮಾನ:

ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ (CAA) 2019 ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯಾಪಕ ಚರ್ಚೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿವಾದಗಳಿಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ತೀರ್ಮಾನವನ್ನು ಈ ಕೆಳಕಂಡಂತೆ ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಮೊದಲನೆಯದಾಗಿ ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ಜಾರಿಗೆ ತರುವ ನಡುವೆ ತಾರತಮ್ಯ ಕಾಣಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ. CAAಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಹಿಂಸೆ ಅನುಭವಿಸಿರುವ

ಪಾಕಿಸ್ತಾನ, ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶ, ಮತ್ತು ಅಫಘಾನಿಸ್ತಾನ ಮೂಲದ ಹಿಂದೂ, ಸಿಖ್, ಬೌದ್ಧ, ಜೈನ್, ಪಾರ್ಸಿ ಮತ್ತು ಕ್ರೈಸ್ತ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಜನತೆಗೆ ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುವುದು. ಆದರೆ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ ಧರ್ಮಿಯರು ಮಾತ್ರ ಹೊರತಾದ ಕಾರಣದಿಂದ ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಚರ್ಚೆಗೆ ಒಳಗಾಗಿದೆ. ಮುಂದುವರಿದು ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಗೆ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗಳು ಎದುರಾಗಿವೆ. CAA ಯು ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಸಮಾನತೆ ಹಕ್ಕು (ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 14) ಮತ್ತು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯದ ಹಕ್ಕು (ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 25)ನ್ನು ಉಲ್ಲಂಘಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬ ಆರೋಪ ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಹೀಗಾಗಿ ಸುಪ್ರೀಂ ಕೋರ್ಟ್ ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಿಕತೆಯ ಕುರಿತು ತೀರ್ಪು ನೀಡಬೇಕಿದೆ. ಈ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಪರಿಣಾಮವನ್ನುಂಟು ಮಾಡಿ, ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ದೇಶಾದ್ಯಂತ ಪ್ರತಿಭಟನೆಗಳು ನಡೆದಿವೆ, ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಈಶಾನ್ಯ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ, ಜನಸಂಖ್ಯಾತ್ಮಕ ಬದಲಾವಣೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಸಂಪತ್ತಿನ ಹಂಚಿಕೆಯ ಭಯ ವ್ಯಕ್ತವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಆಂತರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳು ವ್ಯಕ್ತವಾಗಿವೆ. ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಆಂತರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ರಿಯೆ ವ್ಯಕ್ತವಾಗಿದೆ ಈ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ನಿರಾಶ್ರಿತರ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ, ಎಲ್ಲ ಧರ್ಮಗಳ ಶೋಷಿತ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳನ್ನು (ಉದಾ: ರೋಹಿಂಗ್ಯಾ ಅಥವಾ ಅಹಮದಿಯಾ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಮರು) ಒಳಗೊಂಡರೆ, ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಸಮನ್ವಯಗೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದಿತ್ತು ಎಂಬ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯ ವ್ಯಕ್ತವಾಗಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಭಾರತದ ಧರ್ಮ ನಿರಪೇಕ್ಷತೆಯ ತತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಧಕ್ಕೆ ಉಂಟು ಮಾಡುವ ಹಾಗೂ ಕೆಲವು ನಿರಾಶ್ರಿತ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊರಗಿರುವ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ವಿಶ್ವದ ಇತರ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳಿಂದ ಟೀಕೆಗಳಿಗೂ ಒಳಗಾಗಿದೆ.

ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆಯಾಗಿ ಈ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ನಿರಾಶ್ರಿತರ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸುವುದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಧರ್ಮಗಳ ಶೋಷಿತ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳ (ಉದಾ: ರೋಹಿಂಗ್ಯಾ, ಅಹಮದಿಯಾ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಮರು) ಒಳಗೊಂಡಂತೆ ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಸಮನ್ವಯಗೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದಿತ್ತು.

ಉಪಸಂಹಾರ:

ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ 2019 ಮಾನವೀಯ ನೆಲಗಟ್ಟಿನ ಉದ್ದೇಶವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ, ಆದರೆ ಧರ್ಮ ಆಧಾರಿತ ಶ್ರೇಣೀಕರಣವು ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಧರ್ಮನಿರಪೇಕ್ಷತೆ ತತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ದಕ್ಕೆ ಉಂಟುಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟತೆ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಂವಾದ, ಮತ್ತು ಅನೇಕರನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿದೆ.

ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ 2019 ಮಾನವೀಯ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ರಕ್ಷಿಸುವ ಸಂಕಲ್ಪವನ್ನು ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸುವಂತಾದರೂ, ಅದು ಮುಸ್ಲಿಮರನ್ನು ಹೊರತುಪಡಿಸಿರುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ಎನ್‌ಆರ್‌ಸಿಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧ ಇದೆ ಎಂಬ ಸಾಧ್ಯತೆ ಗಂಭೀರ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಎತ್ತುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಾಗೂ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಮುಂದಿನ ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳು ಅದನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಗೊಳಿಸಲಾಗುತ್ತವೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರ ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ಧ್ವನಿಗಳಿಗೆ ತಕ್ಕ ಸದುತ್ತರವನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬುದರ ಮೇಲೆ ಅವಲಂಬಿತವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಗಳು

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5. ಸುಪ್ರೀಂ ಕೋರ್ಟ್ ಪ್ರಕರಣಗಳು: CAA ವಿರೋಧಿಸಿ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಲಾದ ಕಾನೂನು ಹೋರಾಟಗಳು.

6. ಪ್ರತಿಭಟನೆ ವರದಿಗಳು: ದ ಹಿಂದು, ಇಂಡಿಯನ್ ಎಕ್ಸ್‌ಪ್ರೆಸ್, ಬಿಬಿಸಿ ಮೊದಲಾದ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಕಟಿತ ವಿಷಯಗಳು.
7. ಜಾಗತಿಕ ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳು: ಸಂಯುಕ್ತ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆ (UN) ಮತ್ತು ಮನುಷ್ಯ ಹಕ್ಕು ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಿಂದ ದೊರೆತ ಟೀಕೆಗಳು.

ಗ್ರಂಥಮಣಿ

- ರಾಜಾರಾಮ ತಲ್ಲೂಕು ಏನಿದು ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ನವಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ - 2020
- ಬಿ.ವಿ.ವೈಕುಂಟ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಪೌರತ್ವ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಸಹ್ಯಾದ್ರಿ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ ಮೈಸೂರು - 2021
- ಡಾ.ಎಸ್.ಕೆ.ಶಿವಕುಮಾರ್, ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಮತ್ತು ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಮಂಡ್ಯ ನಂದಿ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ - 2020
- ಪ್ರಸಾದ್ ಹೊಸಕೋಟೆ ಸಂವಿಧಾನಕ್ಕೆ ವಿರುದ್ಧವೋ ? ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ 2019 ಉಡುಪಿ ಪಾರಿಜಾತ ಪುಸ್ತಕ ಭವನ 2021
- ಅನಂತ ಶೆಟ್ಟಿ ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಭಾರತ ಒಂದು ವಿಮರ್ಶೆ ಮಂಗಳೂರು ವಿದ್ಯಾಸೌರಭ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ 2022

ANALYSIS OF SECURITY DEPOSIT IN LOK SABHA ELECTIONS**Dr. Virupakshappa Y. K***Associate Professor of Political Science**Mahantswamy Arts, Science and Commerce College, Haunsbhavi**Haunsbhavi-Post, Hirekerur-tq, Haveri-Dist - 581109**State of Karnataka**Mobile No – 9739297902**Email-virupakshappayk@gmail.com***ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭದ್ರತಾ ಠೇವಣಿಯ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆ**

ಡಾ. ವಿರುಪಾಕ್ಷಪ್ಪ ವಾಯ್.ಕೆ., ಸಹಪ್ರಾಧ್ಯಾಪಕರು ಮತ್ತು ಮುಖ್ಯಸ್ಥರು, ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ವಿಭಾಗ, ಮಹಾಂತಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಕಲಾ, ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಹಾಗೂ ವಾಣಿಜ್ಯ ಮಹಾವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ, ಹಂಪಿ, ಹಾವೇರಿ-ಜಿಲ್ಲೆ

ಸಾರಾಂಶ:

ಜಗತ್ತಿನಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ದೊಡ್ಡ ಸಂಸದೀಯ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ದೇಶ ಭಾರತವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿಯವರೆಗೆ 18 ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಯಶಸ್ವಿಯಾಗಿ ಜರುಗಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾಲಕಾಲಕ್ಕೆ ಮತದಾರರು ತಮ್ಮ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವರ್ತಿಸುವುದರ ಮೂಲಕ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಬದಲಾವಣೆ ಮತ್ತು ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ನಿರ್ಣಾಯಕ ಪಾತ್ರ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇಂತಹ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅನರ್ಹ, ಯೋಗ್ಯರಲ್ಲದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಮತನೀಡಲು ನಿರಾಕರಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅದರ ಪರಿಣಾಮವಾಗಿ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಜರುಗಿದ್ದ ಮೊದಲ ಮೂರು ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭದ್ರತಾ ಠೇವಣಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡವರ ಪ್ರಮಾಣ ಶೇ. 50 ರ ಒಳಗಿತ್ತು. ಅದು ಇಂದು ಶೇ. 85ಕ್ಕೆ ಬಂದು ತಲುಪಿದೆ. ಅದರಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗಿಂತ ಭದ್ರತಾ ಠೇವಣಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವವರಲ್ಲಿ ಇತರರ ಪ್ರಮಾಣ ದುಪ್ಪಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಅಂಕಿಅಂಶಗಳು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ಸಶಕ್ತಗೊಳಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಹಲವು ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹುಟ್ಟುಹಾಕಿವೆ. ಈ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಅನುಭವವುಳ್ಳ, ಜನಸೇವೆ ಮಾಡಲು ಇಚ್ಛಿಸುವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಮನಸ್ಥಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವುದು ಸೂಕ್ತವಾದುದು.

ಪೀಠಿಕೆ:

ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಿಲ್ಲದ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ಊಹಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಿಲ್ಲ. ಇಂದಿನ ಬಹುತೇಕ ಆಧುನಿಕ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿವೆ. ಇದೊಂದು ಅತ್ಯುತ್ತಮ ಮಾದರಿಯ ಸರ್ಕಾರವಾಗಿದ್ದು; ಚರ್ಚೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿಮರ್ಶೆಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಆಡಳಿತದ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯು ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಇಂತಹ ಆಡಳಿತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಆಳುವವರು ಮತ್ತು ಆಳಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವವರು ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳೆ ಆಗಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇಂದಿನ ಆಧುನಿಕ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳು ವಿಶಾಲವಾದ ಭೂಪ್ರದೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ಅಪಾರವಾದ ಜನಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಭಾರತವನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಂತೆ ಜಗತ್ತಿನ ಹಲವು ದೇಶಗಳು ಅಪ್ರತ್ಯಕ್ಷ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿವೆ. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾಲಕಾಲಕ್ಕೆ ನಡೆಯುವ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾರರು ಮತದಾನದ ಮೂಲಕ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ರಚನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗವು ದ್ವಿಸದನಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಕೆಳಮನೆಯಾದ ಲೋಕಸಭೆಯು ನೇರವಾಗಿ ಜನತೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಸುವ ಸದನವಾಗಿದ್ದು, 25 ವರ್ಷ ವಯೋಮಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ ಭಾರತೀಯರು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಅರ್ಹತೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ನಾಮಪತ್ರ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸುವಾಗ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಮೊತ್ತವನ್ನು ಭದ್ರತಾ ಠೇವಣಿಯನ್ನಾಡುವುದು ಕಡ್ಡಾಯವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಯಶಸ್ವಿಯು ನ್ಯಾಯಯುತ, ನಿಷ್ಪಕ್ಷಪಾತ ಮುಕ್ತ ಮತ್ತು ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಅವಲಂಬಿಸಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದರ ಚೊತೆಗೆ ಆ ದೇಶದ ಜನಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳ ನಾಯಕತ್ವ ಮತ್ತು ಗುಣಸ್ವಭಾವ ಹಾಗೂ ಮತದಾರರ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದಲೇ ಡಾ. ಬಿ.ಆರ್. ಅಂಬೇಡ್ಕರರು “ಕೆಟ್ಟ ಸಂವಿಧಾನವು ಉತ್ತಮ ಜನಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದರೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ಸಂವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದಿರುವರು”.

ಭದ್ರತಾ ಠೇವಣಿ :

ಜನತಾ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ 1951ರ 34, 1(ಎ) ಸೆಕ್ಷನ್ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ವರ್ಗದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು 34, 1(ಬಿ) ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿ, ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಸಂಸತ್ತಿನ ಅಥವಾ ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವಾಗ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಮೊತ್ತವನ್ನು ಭದ್ರತಾ ಠೇವಣಿಯನ್ನಾಡುವುದು ಕಡ್ಡಾಯವಾಗಿದೆ. 1951-52 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ವರ್ಗದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು ರೂಪಾಯಿ 500 ಹಾಗೂ ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿ, ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು ರೂಪಾಯಿ 250 ಠೇವಣಿಯಾಗಿ ಇಡಬೇಕಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಜನಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿ (ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ) ಕಾಯ್ದೆ, 2003 ರ ಪ್ರಕಾರ 2009 ರಿಂದ ಭದ್ರತಾ ಠೇವಣಿಯ ಮೊತ್ತವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ . ಸಂಸತ್ತಿನ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ವರ್ಗದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು 25,000 ರೂಪಾಯಿಗಳನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗಗಳ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ವರ್ಗದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು 10,000 ರೂಪಾಯಿಗಳನ್ನು ನಾಮಪತ್ರವನ್ನು ಸಲ್ಲಿಸುವ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಠೇವಣಿಯಾಗಿ ಇಡಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಅದರಂತೆ ಮೇಲಿನ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವ ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಜಾತಿ, ಪರಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಪಂಗಡದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಕ್ರಮವಾಗಿ (ಮೇಲೆ ಸೂಚಿಸಿದಂತೆ) ಅದರ ಅರ್ಧದಷ್ಟು ಮೊತ್ತವನ್ನು ಠೇವಣಿಯಾಗಿ ಇಡಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದಕ್ಕೆ 'ಭದ್ರತಾ ಠೇವಣಿ' ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯಲಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಇದರ ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಗಂಭೀರತೆಯುಳ್ಳ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಮಾತ್ರ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡುವುದು ಹಾಗೂ ಅವರ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧೆಯನ್ನು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸುವುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಸಂಸತ್ತಿನಿಂದ ಅಂಗೀಕರಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟ 1950 ಮತ್ತು 1951ರ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಕಾಲಕಾಲಕ್ಕೆ ತರಲಾದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸುಧಾರಣಾ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಗಳ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಇಂದಿನ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಜರುಗುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಭಾರತದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗವು ಮುಕ್ತ, ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕ ಮತ್ತು ನ್ಯಾಯಸಮ್ಮತ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವುದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಠೇವಣಿ ಮೊತ್ತದ ಹೆಚ್ಚಳದಂತಹ ಮಹತ್ವದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಗೊಳಿಸಿದೆ.

ಭದ್ರತಾ ಠೇವಣಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಮೂರು ನಿಯಮಗಳಿವೆ:

1. ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು ನಾಮಪತ್ರ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸುವಾಗ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಮೊತ್ತವನ್ನು ಭದ್ರತಾ ಠೇವಣಿಯನ್ನಾಡಬೇಕು.
2. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು 1951ರ 158ನೇ ಸೆಕ್ಷನ್ ಭದ್ರತಾ ಠೇವಣಿಯನ್ನು ಹಿಂದಿರುಗಿಸುವ ವಿಧಾನಗಳನ್ನು ವಿವರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಅವುಗಳೆಂದರೆ,
 - ಎ) ಮತದಾನದಪೂರ್ವ ಉಮೇದುದಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಹಿಂಪಡೆದಾಗ,
 - ಬಿ) ಮತದಾನದಪೂರ್ವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು ಮರಣಹೊಂದಿದರೆ,
 - ಸಿ) ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಗೆದ್ದರೆ,
 - ಡಿ) ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಚಲಾಯಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟ ಒಟ್ಟು ಮತಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನೋಟಾದ ಮತಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊರತುಪಡಿಸಿ 1/6 ಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಮತಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡರೆ,
 - ಇ) ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಗೆದ್ದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು ಒಟ್ಟು ಚಲಾಯಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟ ಮತಗಳಲ್ಲಿ 1/6 ಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮತಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದರೂ, ಆ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು ಭದ್ರತಾ ಠೇವಣಿಯನ್ನು ಹಿಂದಿರುಗಿಸಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.
3. ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಚಲಾಯಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟ ಒಟ್ಟು ಮತಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನೋಟಾದ ಮತಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊರತುಪಡಿಸಿ 1/6 ಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮತಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡರೆ ಆ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯು ಭದ್ರತಾ ಠೇವಣಿಯನ್ನು ಮುಟ್ಟುಗೋಲು ಹಾಕಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ವರ್ಷ	ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ	ಠೇವಣಿಯನ್ನು ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ	ತೇಕಡ	ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು			ಇತರರು		
				ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ	ಠೇವಣಿಯನ್ನು ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ	ತೇಕಡ	ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ	ಠೇವಣಿಯನ್ನು ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ	ತೇಕಡ
1952	1874	745	40	1217	344	28	657	401	61
1957	1519	494	33	919	130	14	600	364	61
1962	1985	856	43	1269	362	29	716	494	69
1967	2369	1203	51	1342	390	29	1027	813	79
1971	2784	1707	61	1223	359	29	1561	1348	86
1977	2439	1356	56	1060	100	9	1379	1256	91
1980	4629	3417	74	1541	444	29	3088	2973	96
1984-85	5492	4382	80	1307	387	30	4185	3995	95
1989	6160	5003	81	1378	421	31	4782	4582	96
1991-92	8749	7539	86	1855	840	45	6894	6699	97
1996	13952	12688	91	1817	897	49	12135	11791	97
1998	4750	3486	73	1493	637	43	3257	2849	87
1999	4648	3400	73	1299	437	34	3349	2963	88
2004	5435	4218	78	1351	541	40	4084	3677	90
2009	8070	6829	85	1623	779	48	6447	6050	94
2014	8251	7000	84	1591	807	51	6660	6193	93
2019	8054	6923	85.95	1454	670	46	6600	6253	94
2024	8360	7193	86	1360	565	41	--	--	--

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಜರುಗಿದ್ದ ಮೊದಲ ಮೂರು ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಠೇವಣಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡವರ ಪ್ರಮಾಣ ಶೇ. 50 ರೊಳಗೆ ಇತ್ತು. 1996 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಗರಿಷ್ಠ 12688 ರಷ್ಟು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಅಂದರೆ ಶೇ. 91, 2014 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಶೇ. 84 ರಷ್ಟು, 2019 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಶೇ. 85.95 ಮತ್ತು 2024 ರ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಶೇ. 86 ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಠೇವಣಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇದರಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲವರು ಎರಡೆರಡು ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಿಂದ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿ ಎರಡು ಕಡೆ ಸೋತು ಎರಡು ಕಡೆಯೂ ಠೇವಣಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಈ ಅಂಕಿಅಂಶಗಳು ನಿರಂತರವಾಗಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಠೇವಣಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿರುವ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ ಏರುತ್ತಲೇ ಸಾಗುತ್ತಿರುವುದನ್ನು ದೃಢಪಡಿಸುತ್ತವೆ ಅಲ್ಲದೇ ದುರ್ಬಲ ನಾಯಕತ್ವ ಹೊಂದಿದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಅಥವಾ ನಾನು ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿದ್ದೆ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಸಾಬೀತುಪಡಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಅಲ್ಲದೆ, ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ಸಶಕ್ತಗೊಳಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಹಲವು ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹುಟ್ಟುಹಾಕುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು, ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಇತರ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗಿಂತ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಠೇವಣಿ ಉಳಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ತಮ ಸಾಧನೆ ಮಾಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. 1951-52ರ ಪ್ರಥಮ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿದ್ದ 1217 ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ 344 ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಅಂದರೆ ಶೇ. 28ರಷ್ಟು, 1957ರ ದ್ವಿತೀಯ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿದ್ದ 919 ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ 130 ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಅಂದರೆ ಶೇ. 14ರಷ್ಟು, 3ನೇ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಶೇ. 29, 4ನೇ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಶೇ. 29, 2024ರ 18ನೇ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಶೇ. 41ರಷ್ಟು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಠೇವಣಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. 1977ರ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಶೇ. 9 ರಷ್ಟು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಠೇವಣಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದು; ಇಲ್ಲಿಯವರೆಗಿನ ಕಡಿಮೆ ಪ್ರಮಾಣದ ದಾಖಲೆಯಾಗಿದ್ದರೆ, 2014ರ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಶೇ. 51ರಷ್ಟು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಠೇವಣಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದು ಇಲ್ಲಿಯವರೆಗಿನ ಗರಿಷ್ಠ ದಾಖಲೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಅಂಕಿಅಂಶಗಳು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಇತರರಿಗಿಂತ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷದ ಮೂಲಕ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿದ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿ ಬೆಂಬಲಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ.

ಪ್ರಾದೇಶಿಕ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು, ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಇತರರನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಂತೆ ಪ್ರಥಮ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಶೇ. 61ರಷ್ಟು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಠೇವಣಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಮೇಲಿನ ಕೋಷ್ಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವರಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಈ ಪ್ರಮಾಣ ಏರುಗತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಗುತ್ತಿದ್ದು, ಅದು ಗರಿಷ್ಠ 2009 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಶೇ. 94ರಷ್ಟು ಮತ್ತು 2024 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಶೇ. 94ರಷ್ಟು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಠೇವಣಿ ಮುಟ್ಟುಗೋಲು ಹಾಕಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಅಂದರೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಬಿತ್ತುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ತಾವು ಕೂಡ ಯೋಗ್ಯ ನಾಯಕ ಎಂಬುವುದನ್ನು ಸಾಬೀತುಪಡಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಇವರು ಬಹುಪಾಲು ವಿಫಲರಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆಂದು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಯೋಗ್ಯ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯ ಆಯ್ಕೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧೆ ಇರುವುದರಿಂದ ಬಹಳಷ್ಟು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸಿ ಶೇಕಡ 6 ರಷ್ಟು ಮತಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗದಿರುವಂತಹ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಯು ಕುರುಡರಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಮೆಳ್ಳ ಶೇಷ ಎನ್ನುವ ಗಾಢ ಮಾತಿನಂತೆ ಮತದಾರರು ತಮ್ಮ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಯನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇಂತಹ ಆಯ್ಕೆಯ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳಿಂದ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ಸಶಕ್ತಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಠೇವಣಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿ ಅಥವಾ ಪಕ್ಷಕ್ಕೆ ಹಿನ್ನಡೆಯೆಂದು ಗುರ್ತಿಸಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಭವಿಷ್ಯದ ಅಥವಾ ಮುಂದಿನ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಿಸದಂತೆ ನಿರುತ್ತಾಹಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಕಾರಣವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದನ್ನು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ನಾಯಕತ್ವದ ಕೊರತೆ ಎಂದು ಭಾವಿಸಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಠೇವಣಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದನ್ನು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ವೈಫಲ್ಯದ ಸಂಕೇತವಾಗಿಯೂ ನೋಡಲಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ. 1971ರ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪಕ್ಷೇತರರು ಮಾತ್ರವಲ್ಲ, ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಅಧಿಕೃತ ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗಳಾಗಿ ಕಣಕ್ಕಿಳಿದು, ಠೇವಣಿ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡಿರುವವರ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ ಶೇ. 61 ರಷ್ಟು ದೊಡ್ಡ ಪ್ರಮಾಣದಲ್ಲಿತ್ತು. ಇದನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯುಕ್ತರಾಗಿದ್ದ ಸುಕುಮಾರ್ ಸೇನ್ ಅವರು “ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಯ ಆಯ್ಕೆಯ ವಿಚಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಎಚ್ಚರಿಕೆವಹಿಸದಿದ್ದರೆ ಅಂಥ ಪಕ್ಷ ಮತ್ತು ಅಭ್ಯರ್ಥಿಗೆ ಪಾಠ ಕಳಿಸಲು ಮತದಾರರು ಹಿಂಜರಿಯುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂಬುವುದು ಇದರಿಂದ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಪಟ್ಟಿದ್ದರು .

ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವು ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯು ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಮುಕ್ತ ಅವಕಾಶವನ್ನು ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಿಕೊಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದರೆ, ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಮತಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲಾಗದ ಸ್ಥಿತಿ ಏರ್ಪಟ್ಟಿರುವುದು, ಪ್ರಬಲ ಪ್ರೇರೋಚಿ ಏರ್ಪಡದಿರುವಿಕೆ, ಇಂದಿನ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮತದಾರರ ಅರ್ಥದಷ್ಟು ಮತಗಳಿಗೆ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯ ಇಲ್ಲದಂತಾಗುವುದು ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ದುರ್ಬಲಗೊಳಿಸುವುದರಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಶಯವಿಲ್ಲ. ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿ ಹಣಬಲ, ಜಾತಿಬಲದಂತಹ ನಕರಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಂಶಗಳು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆ ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಪರೋಕ್ಷವಾಗಿ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಮತಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲಾರದ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಏರ್ಪಡಿಸಿ ಭದ್ರತಾ ಠೇವಣಿಯ ಮುಟ್ಟುಗೋಲಿಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗುತ್ತವೆ. ಮತದಾರರ ನಡುವಣಿಕೆಯು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸಮಾಜೀಕರಣದ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಯನ್ನು ಸೂಚಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಗ್ರಹಿಸಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಅಲ್ಲದೇ ಗಣ್ಯರು ಮತ್ತು ಜನಸಾಮಾನ್ಯರಲ್ಲಿನ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಆಂತರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ. “ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಮಟ್ಟದ ಮತದಾನದ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾತಿಯ ಐಕ್ಯಮತ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಅಂಶವಾಗಿದೆ. ದೊಡ್ಡ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಜಾತಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಜಾತಿಯ ಗೌರವಾನ್ವಿತ ಸದಸ್ಯನನ್ನು ಅಥವಾ ಅವರ ಜಾತಿಯ ಸದಸ್ಯರನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸುವ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷವನ್ನು ಬೆಂಬಲಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆಂದು ಪಾಲ್ ಆರ್. ಬ್ರಾಸ್ ಅವರು ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಪಟ್ಟಿದ್ದಾರೆ . ರಜನಿ

ನಾಡಿಗೆ ವರ್ತಕ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರ ಕೊಡುಗೆಗಳು

ಡಾ. ನಾಗಮ್ಮ ಹೆಚ್.ಎನ್.

ಇತಿಹಾಸ ಸಹಾಯಕ ಪ್ರಾಧ್ಯಾಪಕರು

ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಪ್ರಥಮ ದರ್ಜೆ ಕಾಲೇಜು, ಕುಣಿಗಲ್.

ಪೀಠಿಕೆ: ದೇಶದ ಹಾಗೂ ನಾಡಿನ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರಿಗೆ ವಿಶೇಷವಾದ ಸ್ಥಾನವಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಸ್ತ್ರೀಗೆ ಹೋಲಿಸಿರುವ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ ನಮ್ಮದು. ಪುರುಷನ ಜೀವನ ಪರಿಪೂರ್ಣತೆಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಪಾತ್ರ ಪ್ರಧಾನವಾಗಿರುವುದನ್ನು ನಮ್ಮ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯು ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರು ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕಾಲದಿಂದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತದವರೆಗೆ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ತಮ್ಮನ್ನು ತೊಡಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವುದು ಅಗಣಿತ ವಿಚಾರವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದು ಸಮಾಜದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ವರ್ಗಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಭಿನ್ನಭೇದವಿಲ್ಲದೆ ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಲೇಖನದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ವರ್ತಕ ಸಮುದಾಯಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿದ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಹಾಗೂ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕೊಡುಗೆಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ಚರ್ಚಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.

ಹಿಂದೂ ಮತ್ತು ಜೈನ ಸ್ಮಾರಕಗಳ ನಿರ್ಮಾಣ ಮತ್ತು ದಾನ-ದತ್ತಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವರ್ತಕ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರು:

ನಾಡಿನ ವರ್ತಕ ಕುಟುಂಬಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿದ ಹೆಣ್ಣುಮಕ್ಕಳು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ತಮ್ಮನ್ನು ತೊಡಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವುದು ಅಧ್ಯಯನದಿಂದ ತಿಳಿದುಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕವಾಗಿ ಸ್ಮಾರಕಗಳ ನಿರ್ಮಾಣ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳು, ದಾನ-ದತ್ತಿಗಳಂತಹ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹಿಂದೆ ಉಳಿದಿರಲಿಲ್ಲ. ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕವಾಗಿ ಇಲ್ಲವೆ ತಮ್ಮ ಗಂಡಂದಿರ ಜೊತೆಗೂಡಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ತೊಡಗಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದರು.

ವ್ಯಾಪಾರ ಮತ್ತು ವಾಣಿಜ್ಯದ ಕಾರಣದಿಂದಾಗಿ ಆರ್ಥಿಕವಾಗಿ ಸದೃಢರಾದ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರು ದೇವಾಲಯಗಳು, ಬಸದಿಗಳು, ಸ್ತಂಭಗಳು, ಮಂಟಪಗಳಂತಹ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಸ್ಮಾರಕಗಳ ನಿರ್ಮಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ತಮ್ಮನ್ನು ತೊಡಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದರು. ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ. 1033ರಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜೇಂದ್ರ ಚೋಳನ ಆಳ್ವಿಕೆಯ ಅವಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ನಂಜನಗೂಡಿನ ಮಾರಯ್ಯಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಮಡದಿ ಗುಂಡಬ್ಬೆಯು ಸುತ್ತೂರಿನ(ಸ್ತ್ರೋತ್ರಿಯೂರು) ಮೂಲಸ್ಥಾನ ದೇವರ ಗುಡಿಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸಿ, ಭೂಮಿಯನ್ನು ಕ್ರಯಕ್ಕೆ ಕೊಂಡು ದಾನವಾಗಿ ನೀಡಿದಳೆಂದು ಸುತ್ತೂರು ಮಠದ ಶಾಸನವು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ.1094ರ ಚಿಕ್ಕಬೆಮ್ಮತಿಯ ಶಾಸನದಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿಸಿರುವಂತೆ ವರ್ತಕ ಅಹಿತರ ರೇಚಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಮೊಮ್ಮಗಳು ಚಾರುವಕಬ್ಬೆಯು ತನ್ನ ತಾತ ನಿರ್ಮಿಸಿದ ಪೊಲ್ಲೇಶ್ವರ ದೇವಾಲಯಕ್ಕೆ ನಂದಿ ಮಂಟಪವೊಂದನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸಿದಳು. ಅಲ್ಲದೆ ಆ ದೇವಾಲಯಕ್ಕೆ ನಂದಿ, ಭೈರವ, ಭಗವತಿ, ನಾರಾಯಣ ವಿಗ್ರಹಗಳನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸಿಕೊಡುವುದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ದೇವಾಲಯಕ್ಕೆ ಸುಣ್ಣವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿಸಿದಳು. ಈ ದೇವಾಲಯವನ್ನು ಗಂಡನಾರಾಯಣಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಮಗ ಲಕಣಾಚಾರಿಯು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸಿದ್ದನು. ದೊಡ್ಡಗದ್ದವಳ್ಳಿಯ ಮಹಾಲಕ್ಷ್ಮಿ ದೇವಾಲಯದ ನಿರ್ಮಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ವರ್ತಕ ಕುಲ್ಲಹಣರಾವುತನ ಜೊತೆಗೂಡಿ ಆತನ ಪತ್ನಿ ಸಹಜಾದೇವಿಯು ಪ್ರಧಾನ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸಿದ್ದಳು. ದೊಡ್ಡಗದ್ದವಳ್ಳಿಯ ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ.1113ರ ಶಾಸನವು ಈಕೆಯನ್ನು ಅವನ 'ಅರ್ಧಾಂಗ ಶರೀರಿಯರಪ್ಪ' ಎಂದು ಹೊಗಳಿದೆ. ಈ ಅಂಶವು ಕುಲ್ಲಹಣರಾವುತನ ಸಾಧನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ

ಸಹಜಾದೇವಿಯ ಪಾತ್ರವೇನೆಂಬುದನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ದೋರಸಮುದ್ರದ ಪಟ್ಟಣಸ್ವಾಮಿಯಾದ ನೊಳಂಬಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಪತ್ನಿ ದೇವಿಕಬ್ಬೆಯು ಕತ್ತರಿಘಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ತ್ರಿಕೂಟ ಜಿನಾಲಯವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸಿ ಅರ್ಹನಹಳ್ಳಿ ಗ್ರಾಮವನ್ನು, ಎರಡು ಎಣ್ಣೆ ಗಾಣಗಳು, ಎರಡು ಮನೆಗಳು, ಎರಡು ಹೂದೋಟಗಳನ್ನು ದಾನವಾಗಿ ನೀಡಿದಳು ಎಂದು ಹೊಸಹೊಳಲಿನ ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ.1118 ರ ಶಾಸನವು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ. 1142ರಲ್ಲಿ ಹೊಯ್ಸಳ ವಿಷ್ಣುವರ್ಧನನ ಆಳ್ವಿಕೆಯ ಅವಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ತೆಲ್ಲಿಗ ಸಮುದಾಯಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿದ ಜಕ್ಕವ್ವೆ ಎಂಬಾಕೆಯು ತನ್ನ ಮೃತ ಸಹೋದರ ಅಜ್ಜಮನ ನೆನಪಿಗಾಗಿ ಕೆಲ್ಲಂಗೇರಿಯಲ್ಲಿ (ಹರಿಹರಪುರ) ಶಿವಲಿಂಗವನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠಾಪಿಸಿ ಗ್ರಾಮೇಶ್ವರ ಎಂಬ ಹೆಸರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿವದೇವಾಲಯವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸಿದಳು. ಈ ದೇವಾಲಯವು ತೆಲ್ಲಿಗರ ಕುಲಕ್ಕೆ ಕಳಶಪ್ರಾಯದಂತಿತ್ತು. ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ.1392ರಲ್ಲಿ ಗೇರುಸೊಪ್ಪೆಯ ವರ್ತಕ ವೋಜಣ್ಣಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಮಡದಿ ರಾಮಕ್ಕ ಗೇರುಸೊಪ್ಪೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅನಂತತೀರ್ಥ ಚೈತ್ಯಾಲಯವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸಿ ದೇವರ ಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠಾಪನೆ ಮಾಡಿದಳು. ಹಂಪಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸಿರಿಗಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಮಡದಿ ಮಾಟಮ್ಮ ಉಯ್ಯಾಲೆ ಕಂಬಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿಸಿದಳು ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿ ಹಂಪಿಯಲ್ಲಿರುವ ತೆಲುಗು ಶಾಸನವೊಂದು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ವರ್ತಕ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಸ್ಮಾರಕಗಳಲ್ಲದೆ ಲೌಕಿಕ ಸ್ಮಾರಕಗಳ ನಿರ್ಮಾಣದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಆಸಕ್ತಿ ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದರೆಂಬುದು ತಿಳಿಯುತ್ತದೆ.

ವರ್ತಕ ಹಾಗೂ ಕಸುಬುದಾರಿ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರು ದೇವಾಲಯಗಳು ಹಾಗೂ ಬಸದಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಅಪಾರ ಪ್ರಮಾಣ ದಾನ-ದತ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ.1130ರ ಶ್ರವಣಬೆಳಗೊಳದ ಶಾಸನದಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿಸಿರುವ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಅಯ್ಯಾವೊಳೆಯ ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧ ಜೈನವರ್ತಕ ಮಲ್ಲಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಮಡದಿ ಚಟ್ಟಕಬ್ಬೆಯು ಜೈನಧರ್ಮದ ನಿಷ್ಠಾವಂತ ಅನುಯಾಯಿಯಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಅನೇಕ ಜೈನಬಸದಿಗಳಿಗೆ, ಜೈನಮುನಿಗಳಿಗೆ, ಅವರ ಆಹಾರ, ವಸತಿ, ಭೈಷಜ್ಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣಕ್ಕೆ ಅಪಾರವಾದ ದಾನ-ದತ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದಳು. ಸಿಂದವಾಡಿಯ ಸೋದರಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಗರುಡಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಮಡದಿ ಬೋಜಬ್ಬೆಯು ರಾಮದುರ್ಗದ ಸೋಮೇಶ್ವರ ದೇವರ ನಂದಾದೀವಿಗೆಗೆ ಹಾಗೂ ನಿತ್ಯನೈವೇದ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಭೂಮಿಯನ್ನು ದಾನವಾಗಿ ನೀಡಿದಳು. ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ. 1237ರಲ್ಲಿ ದೋರಸಮುದ್ರದ ಮಾಲೆಗಾರನಾದ ಬಿಟ್ಟಯ್ಯನ ಮಗಳು ಹೊಯ್ಸಳೇಶ್ವರ ದೇವರಿಗೆ ಒಂದು ಗದ್ಯಾಣವನ್ನು ದಾನವಾಗಿ ನೀಡಿದಳು. ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ. 1378ರ ಪಡುವಾರಿ (ಕುಂದಾಪುರ ತಾ.) ಶಾಸನದಲ್ಲಿ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸಿರುವಂತೆ ಹೊಯ್ಸಳ ಮಹಾಪ್ರಧಾನ ಬಾರಕೂರು ರಾಜ್ಯವನ್ನು ಆಳುತ್ತಿರಲು ಶ್ರೀಮತ್ ವಿದ್ಯಾನಾಥದೇವರಿಗೆ ಬಯಿದೂರು (ಬೈಂದೂರು) ನಾಡ ಬೀರಣ್ಣಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಮೊಮ್ಮಗಳು ಕುಂಚುಕಬ್ಬೆಯು ವರ್ತಕರಾದ ಕೋಟಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿ ಮತ್ತು ಗೋವಿಂದಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಜೊತೆಗೂಡಿ ಭೂಮಿಯನ್ನು ದಾನವಾಗಿ ನೀಡಿದರು. ಶಾಸನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯದ ಕುರಿತು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟವಾದ ಯಾವುದೇ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಗಳಿಲ್ಲದಿದ್ದರೂ ಆಕೆಯ ಕೊಡುಗೆಗಳು, ನಿರ್ಮಾಣಗಳು, ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ದಾನ-ದತ್ತಿಗಳು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕವಾಗಿ ಆಕೆಗೆ ಒಂದು ಉನ್ನತ ಸ್ಥಾನ-ಮಾನವನ್ನು ತಂದುಕೊಟ್ಟಿದ್ದವೆಂದು ಹೇಳಬಹುದು.

ಜೈನರಲ್ಲಿನ ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ವಿಧಿಯೆಂದರೆ ಸಲ್ಲೇಖನ ವ್ರತ. ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಶ್ರದ್ಧೆಯುಳ್ಳ ಬಹುಪಾಲು ಜೈನರು ಸಲ್ಲೇಖನ ವ್ರತದಿಂದ ಸದ್ಗತಿ ಪಡೆಯುತ್ತಿದ್ದನ್ನು ಜೈನಧರ್ಮದಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾಣುತ್ತೇವೆ. ಈ ಪದ್ಧತಿ ಜೈನವರ್ತಕರಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇದ್ದು ಜೈನ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರು ಸಲ್ಲೇಖನ ವ್ರತವನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದ ಹಲವಾರು ನಿದರ್ಶನಗಳು ನಾಡಿನ ಶಾಸನಗಳ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದಿಂದ ತಿಳಿದು ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ. 1081 ರ ಬನವಾಸಿಯ

ಶಾಸನದಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿಸಿರುವಂತೆ ಜೈನಗುರು ಸಕಳಚಂದ್ರಭಟ್ಟಾರಕರ ಶಿಷ್ಯ ಹಾಗೂ ತಿಪ್ಪಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿ ಸಾತಯ್ಯನ ಮಡದಿಯಾದ ಭೋಗವ್ವೆಯು ಸಮಾಧಿ ವಿಧಿಯಿಂದ ಸದ್ಗತಿ ಹೊಂದಿದಳು. ಬಳ್ಳಿಗಾವೆಯ ಪಟ್ಟಣಸ್ವಾಮಿಯಾದ ಮಾಳಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಪತ್ನಿ ಪದ್ಮವ್ವೆ ಸಲ್ಲೇಖನ ವ್ರತವನ್ನು ಕೈಗೊಂಡು ಸಮಾಧಿ ಹೊಂದಿದಳು. ಈಕೆಯ ನಿಷಿದ್ಧಿಯನ್ನು ಬಳ್ಳಿಗಾವೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠಾಪಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಈಕೆಯನ್ನು ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ. 1206ರ ಬಳ್ಳಿಗಾವೆಯ ಶಾಸನದಲ್ಲಿ ಜೈನಧರ್ಮದ ತವರ್ಮನೆ, ಪತಿಭಕ್ತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸೀತೆ, ಅತ್ತಿಮಬ್ಬೆಯ ಸಮಾನ ಎಂದು ಹೊಗಳಿದೆ. ನೊಂಪಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಮಗ ವೀರಯ್ಯನ ಮಡದಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಜೈನ ಗುರು ಸೋಮದೇವಾಚಾರ್ಯರ ಶಿಷ್ಯ ಕೆಳದಿ-ಅವ್ವೆಯು ಸಮಾಧಿ ವಿಧಿಯಿಂದ (ಸಲ್ಲೇಖನ ವ್ರತ) ದೇಹತ್ಯಾಗ ಮಾಡಿದಾಗ ಆಕೆಯ ನಿಷಿದ್ಧಿಯನ್ನು ಪರೋಕ್ಷವಿನಯವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠಾಪಿಸಲಾಯಿತು ಎಂದು ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ.1267ರ ಅಣ್ಣಿಗೇರಿ ಶಾಸನವು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಜೈನ ವರ್ತಕ ಬಾಮಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ತಾಯಿ ಮಾಳವ್ವೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಆತನ ಮಡದಿ ಬೂಚವ್ವೆಯರು ಬೇರೆ ಬೇರೆ ಕಾಲಾವಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸಲ್ಲೇಖನ ವ್ರತದಿಂದ ನಿಷಿದ್ಧಿಯಾದರು. ನಿಟ್ಟೂರಿನ(ಗುಬ್ಬಿ) ಆದೀಶ್ವರ ಬಸದಿಯ ಬಳಿ ಇವರಿಬ್ಬರ ನಿಷಿದ್ಧಿಗಳನ್ನು ನಿಲ್ಲಿಸಲಾಯಿತು. ಅದೇ ರೀತಿ ಮಾಳವ್ವೆಯ ತಂದೆ ಗುಣದಬೆಡಂಗ ಮಲ್ಲಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಆತನ ಮಗ ಮಾಳೆಯನು ನಿಷಿದ್ಧಿಗಳಾಗಿರುವುದು ನಿಟ್ಟೂರಿನ ಶಾಸನದಿಂದ ತಿಳಿದುಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಈಸೂರಿನ(ಶಿಕಾರಿಪುರ) ಜೈನವರ್ತಕ ದೇವಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿ, ಅವನ ಮಡದಿಯರಾದ ಸೋಮವ್ವೆ ಮತ್ತು ಲಿಂಗವ್ವೆಯರು ಸಲ್ಲೇಖನ ವ್ರತ ಕೈಗೊಂಡು ಸಮಾಧಿಯಾದರು. ಇವರ ನೆನಪಿಗೆ ನಿಷಿದ್ಧಿ ಕಲ್ಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಲಾಯಿತು.

ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ.1130ರ ಶ್ರವಣಬೆಳಗೊಳದ ಶಾಸನದಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿಸಿರುವ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಅಯ್ಯಾವೊಳೆಯ ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧ ಜೈನವರ್ತಕ ದಮ್ಮಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಮಗ ಮಲ್ಲಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ತ್ರಿಭುವನಮಲ್ಲ ಚಲದಂಕರಾಯ ಹೊಯ್ಸಳಸೆಟ್ಟಿ ಎಂಬ ಬಿರುದಿತ್ತು. ಈತನ ಮಡದಿ ಚಟ್ಟಿಕಬ್ಬೆಯು ಜೈನಧರ್ಮದ ನಿಷ್ಠಾವಂತ ಅನುಯಾಯಿಯಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಅನೇಕ ಜೈನಬಸದಿಗಳಿಗೆ, ಜೈನಮುನಿಗಳ ಆಹಾರ, ವಸತಿ, ಭೈಷಜ್ಯಗಳಿಗೆ(ಔಷಧಿ) ಹಾಗೂ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣಕ್ಕೆ ಅಪಾರವಾದ ದಾನ-ದತ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದಳು. ಮಲ್ಲಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿ ಮತ್ತು ಚಟ್ಟಿಕಬ್ಬೆಯು ನಿಷಿದ್ಧಿಯಾದ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಅವರ ಮಗ ಭೂಚಣನು ಇವರಿಬ್ಬರಿಗೂ ನಿಷಿದ್ಧಿಕಲ್ಲನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿಸಿದನು.

ಆಡಳಿತ:

ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ. 1146ರಲ್ಲಿ ಚಾಲುಕ್ಯ ಜಗದೇಕಮಲ್ಲನ ಆಳ್ವಿಕೆಯ ಅವಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಬನವಾಸಿ-12000 ನಾಡಿಗೆ ಸೇರಿದ ಕೊಂಡರಟ್ಟಿ-70ರ ಬಳಿಯ ದೇಸಿವಟ್ಟಣ ಬಾಳೆಹಳ್ಳಿಯನ್ನು ಛಲದಂಕಮಲ್ಲ ಮಲ್ಲಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿ ಮತ್ತು ಅವನ ಪತ್ನಿ ಚಾಮವ್ವೆಯರು ಕೂಡಿ ಆಳುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿದುಬರುವ ಇನ್ನೊಂದು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಅಂಶವೆಂದರೆ ಬಾಳೆಹಳ್ಳಿಯ ಶಾಸನದಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿಸಿರುವಂತೆ ಗಂಡನ ಜೊತೆಗೂಡಿ ಹೆಂಡತಿಯು ಗ್ರಾಮಾಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗಿಯಾಗುತ್ತಿದ್ದಳು. ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ವರ್ಗದ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರ ಸ್ಥಾನಮಾನದ ವಿಷಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಇದೊಂದು ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ ವಿಷಯವಾಗಿದೆ.

ವೀರಶೈವದಲ್ಲಿ ವರ್ತಕ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರು ಕಡಿಮೆಯೇನಿರಲಿಲ್ಲ. ಹಿರೇಕೆರೂರಿನ ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ.1204ರ ಶಾಸನದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾತೇನಹಳ್ಳಿಯ ಕಾಮಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಮಡದಿ ವೆಣ್ಣಿಲಸೆಟ್ಟಿಕವ್ವೆಯು ಕೇವಲ ಮನೆಗೆಲಸಕ್ಕಷ್ಟೇ ತನ್ನನ್ನು ಸೀಮಿತಗೊಳಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳದೆ ಕೈಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕತ್ತಿಹಿಡಿದು ತನ್ನ ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ವ್ಯಾಪಾರಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಕಳ್ಳರು,

ದರೋಡೆಕೋರರಿಂದ ಆಗುತ್ತಿದ್ದ ಸಂಕಷ್ಟವನ್ನು ದೂರಮಾಡಿ ವೀರಬಣಂಜುಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ರಕ್ಷಿಸಿದ ಕೀರ್ತಿಗೆ ಪಾತ್ರಳಾಗಿದ್ದಾಳೆ.

ಗರುಡ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅನೇಕ ವೈಶ್ಯಕುಲ ವೀರರು ರಾಜನಿಗಾಗಿ ಲೆಂಕರಾಗಿರುವುದು ಶಾಸನಗಳಿಂದ ತಿಳಿದುಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ವೈಶ್ಯಕುಲ ವೀರರ ಜೊತೆ ಅವರ ಮಡದಿಯರು ಕೂಡ ಲೆಂಕರಾಗಿರುವುದು ಅವರ ಸ್ವಾಮಿನಿಷ್ಠೆ ಹಾಗೂ ವರ್ತಕ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರ ವೀರತ್ವದ ಗುಣಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಅತ್ಯುತ್ತಮ ನಿದರ್ಶನವೆಂದರೆ ಹೊಯ್ಸಳರ ಆಳ್ವಿಕೆಯ ಅವಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕಬ್ಬಾಹುನಾಡನ್ನು ಆಳುತ್ತಿದ್ದ ಮುಗಿಲಕುಲಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿದವರು ಎಂದು ಶಾಸನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇಳಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಗಂಡನಾರಾಯಣಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ವಂಶಜರೆಲ್ಲ ಅನುವಂಶಿಕವಾಗಿ ಹೊಯ್ಸಳರ ಮಹಾಸಾಮಂತರಾಗಿದ್ದರಲ್ಲದೆ ಹೊಯ್ಸಳ ಅರಸರ ಅನುವಂಶಿಕ ಗರುಡರಾಗಿದ್ದರು. ಈ ಮನೆತನದ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರು ತಮ್ಮ ಗಂಡಂದಿರ ಜೊತೆಗೂಡಿ ಹೊಯ್ಸಳ ಅರಸರಿಗಾಗಿ ಗರುಡರಾಗಿರುವುದು ಶಾಸನಗಳ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದಿಂದ ತಿಳಿದುಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಗಂಡನಾರಾಯಣಸೆಟ್ಟಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಅವನ ಮಡದಿ ಮಾರವ್ವನಾಯಕಿತಿ-ಇವರಿಬ್ಬರು ಐವರು ಮಾನಿಸ ಲೆಂಕರೊಡಗೂಡಿ ಹೊಯ್ಸಳ ಎರೆಯಂಗನಿಗಾಗಿ ಗರುಡರಾದರು. ಗಂಡನಾರಾಯಣಸೆಟ್ಟಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಮಾರವ್ವನಾಯಕಿತಿ ಮಗ ಹೊಯ್ಸಳಸೆಟ್ಟಿ ಮತ್ತು ಮಾಚವ್ವನಾಯಕಿಯು ಐವರು ಮಾನಿಸ ಲೆಂಕರ ಜೊತೆ ಬಿಟ್ಟಿದೇವನಿಗಾಗಿ ಲೆಂಕರಾದರು. ಹೊಯ್ಸಳಸೆಟ್ಟಿ ಮತ್ತು ಮಾಚವ್ವನಾಯಕಿಯು ಮಗ ಕೂರೆಯ ನಾಯಕ ಮತ್ತು ಅವನ ಇಬ್ಬರು ಮಡದಿಯರಾದ ಮಾರವ್ವ ನಾಯಕಿತಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಚಿಕ್ಕಮಾದವ್ವನಾಯಕಿಯರು ಏಳು ಜನ ಲೆಂಕರ ಜೊತೆಗೂಡಿ ನರಸಿಂಹ ದೇವರಸರಿಗಾಗಿ ಲೆಂಕರಾದರು. ಕೂರೆಯ ನಾಯಕನ ಮಗ ಸಿವನೆಯನಾಯಕನು ಐವರು ಲೆಂಕರು ಹಾಗೂ ಮೂವರು ಲೆಂಕಿಯರ ಜೊತೆಗೂಡಿ 2ನೇ ಬಲ್ಲಾಳನಿಗಾಗಿ ಮಡಿದರು. ಸಿವನೆಯ ನಾಯಕನ ಮಗ ಲಕ್ಕೆಯನಾಯಕ ಹಾಗೂ ಅವನ ಮಡದಿ ಗಂಗಾದೇವಿಯು ಇಮ್ಮಡಿ ನರಸಿಂಹದೇವನಿಗಾಗಿ ಗರುಡರಾದರು. ಲಕ್ಕೆಯನಾಯಕನ ಮಗ ಕನ್ನೇಯನಾಯಕನು ತನ್ನ ಮಡದಿಯರಾದ ವೊಮ್ಮವ್ವೆ, ಜವನವ್ವೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಕಲ್ಲವ್ವೆಯರು ಸೇರಿ ಹತ್ತು ಮಾನಿಸ ಲೆಂಕಿಯರು ಮತ್ತು ಇಪ್ಪತ್ತೊಂದು ಮಾನಿಸ ಲೆಂಕರೊಡನೆ ಸೇರಿ ಗಜಮಸ್ತಕದ ಮೇಲೆ ಆರು ಬಾರಿ ಗರುಡವನ್ನಪ್ಪಿ ಸೋಮೇಶ್ವರದೇವನೊಡನೆ ಗರುಡರಾದರು.

ಕನ್ನೇಯನಾಯಕನ ಮಗ ರಂಗೇಯನಾಯಕನು ತನ್ನ ಮಡದಿಯರಾದ ಕೇತವ್ವನಾಯಕಿತಿ, ಹೊನ್ನವ್ವನಾಯಕಿತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಮಂಚವ್ವನಾಯಕಿಯರ ಜೊತೆ ಹತ್ತು ಮಾನಿಸ ಲೆಂಕಿಯರು ಮತ್ತು ಇಪ್ಪತ್ತು ಮಾನಿಸ ಲೆಂಕರ ಜೊತೆಗೂಡಿ ನರಸಿಂಹ ದೇವರಸ(3ನೇ ನರಸಿಂಹ)ರಿಗಾಗಿ ಗಜಮಸ್ತಕದ ಮೇಲೆ ಆರು ಬಾರಿ ಗರುಡವನ್ನಪ್ಪಿ ಲೆಂಕರಾದರು. ಹೀಗೆ ಕಬ್ಬಾಹುನಾಡನ್ನಾಳುತ್ತಿದ್ದ ಹೊಯ್ಸಳ ಮಹಾಸಾಮಂತ ಗಂಡನಾರಾಯಣಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಇಡೀ ವಂಶವೇ ಹೊಯ್ಸಳ ಅರಸರಿಗಾಗಿ ತಮ್ಮ ಜೀವನ ಹಾಗೂ ಪ್ರಾಣವನ್ನು ತೆತ್ತರು. ಲೆಂಕವಾಳಿತನವು ಅನುವಂಶಿಕ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯವಾಗಿರಬಹುದು ಎಂಬ ಡಾ. ಎಂ. ಚಿದಾನಂದಮೂರ್ತಿಯವರ ಮಾತನ್ನು ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸುವುದಾದರೆ ಗಂಡನಾರಾಯಣಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯ ಏಳು ತಲೆಮಾರುಗಳು ಅವರ ಪತ್ನಿಯರ ಜೊತೆಗೂಡಿ ಲೆಂಕರಾದರೆಂಬ ವಿಷಯವು ಲೆಂಕವಾಳಿತನ ಮೆರೆಯುವುದು ಅವರ ವಂಶದ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯವಾಗಿತ್ತೆನ್ನಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಲೆಂಕವಾಳಿತನದಲ್ಲಿ ವರ್ತಕ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರ ಕೊಡುಗೆ ಗಮನಾರ್ಹವಾದುದು.

ಈ ವಂಶಜರನ್ನು ಶಾಸನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಶ್ರೀ ಮನ್ಮುಗಿಲಕುಲಕಮಳಮಾತ್ರ್ಪಂಡರುಂ, ಹೊಯ್ಸಳೇಶ್ವರದೇವ ಪಾದಾರಾವಿಂದ ಮಕರಂದಮತ್ತಭೃಂಗರುಂ, ಶ್ರೀಮನುಮಹಾಸಾಮಂತರುಂ, ಸಮಯದ್ರೋಹನಂ ಮರ್ಧಿಸಿನಾನಾದೇಶಿಯಂ ಸೆಟ್ಟಿವಟ್ಟವರ ತಳೆದ ಗಂಡನಾರಾಯಣರುಂ ಕನ್ನಡಿಗಮೊನೆಯಾಳ್ತನಂಗೆಯ್ವ ನಾಯಕರ್ಗೆ ಸೇನಾನಾಯಕರುಂ, ಬಿರುದರಗೋವರುಂ, ಹೊಯ್ಸಳಲೆಂಕನಿಸ್ಸಂಕರುಂ, ಕಬ್ಬಾಹುನಾಡಾಳ್ವರಂ, ಹಬ್ಬಿಗಾಳೆಗಕ್ಕೆ ಮಲೆವನಾಯಕರ ಗಂಡರಂ, ಸೇವುಣಸೈನ್ಯವಿಭ್ವಾಡನರುಂ, ವೈರಿಸಾಮಂತ ಗರುಡನಾರಾಯಣರುಂ, ಧನಮನಪ್ರಾಣಂಗಳೊಳುಸಿರಗುವಾರುವ ಲೆಂಕರಗಂಡರುಂ- ಹೀಗೆ ಈ ಮನೆತನದವರ ವೀರತ್ವ, ಸ್ವಾಮಿನಿಷ್ಠೆ, ನಾಡಿಗಾಗಿ ತಮ್ಮ ತನು-ಮನ-ಧನಗಳನ್ನು ಸಮರ್ಪಿಸಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಶಾಸನಗಳು ಹಾಡಿ ಹೊಗಳಿವೆ.

ವರ್ತಕ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರಲ್ಲಿ ಸಹಗಮನ ಪದ್ಧತಿ ರೂಢಿಯಲ್ಲಿತ್ತೆಂದು 14ನೇ ಶತಮಾನದ ಅಂಬಳೆಯ ಶಾಸನವೊಂದು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ವರ್ತಕ ತಮ್ಮಿಸೆಟ್ಟಿಯು ಮರಣ ಹೊಂದಿದಾಗ ಆತನ ಪತ್ನಿ ಬೊಮ್ಮಕ್ಕ ಗೋಪೆಯ ಹೊಕ್ಕಳು ಎಂದಿದೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಗೋಪೆ ಎಂದರೆ ಗೋರಿ, ಸಮಾಧಿ ಸ್ಥಳ ಎಂದು ಅರ್ಥ ಕೊಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಅಂದರೆ ಬೊಮ್ಮಕ್ಕ ತನ್ನ ಗಂಡ ಮರಣ ಹೊಂದಿದಾಗ ತನ್ನ ಗಂಡನ ಚೊತೆ ತಾನು ಚಿತೆಯೇರಿದಳು ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿ ಶಾಸನದಿಂದ ತಿಳಿದುಬರುತ್ತದೆ.

ಮೇಲ್ಕಂಡ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ವರ್ತಕರು ಮಾತ್ರವಲ್ಲದೆ ವರ್ತಕ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರೂ ಕೂಡ ನಾಡಿನ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಹಾಗೂ ಆಡಳಿತ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಿಗೆ ಕೊಡುಗೆ ನೀಡುವುದರ ಮೂಲಕ ನಾಡಿನ ಚರಿತ್ರೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಗಣ್ಯಸ್ಥಾನ ಪಡೆದಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

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ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವ ಮತ್ತು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯ: ಒಂದು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ

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ಒಂಭೂಟಿಚಿಫಿಣಿ-

ಧರ್ಮವು ಒಂದಾನೊಂದು ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮಾಜದ ಚಲನಶೀಲ ತತ್ವವಾಗಿ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡಿದೆ. ಧರ್ಮದ ಅಪ್ರಸ್ತುತತೆಯನ್ನು ಅರಿತದ್ದರಿಂದಾಗಿಯೇ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಕ್ರಾಂತಿ ನೆರವೇರಿಸುವ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮ ಬೋಧಿಸಿದ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳಿಗಿಂತ ಉನ್ನತ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಎತ್ತಿ ಹಿಡಿಯಲಾಯಿತು. ಧರ್ಮಕ್ಕಿಂತಲೂ ಉನ್ನತ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಅವಿಭಾಜ್ಯ ಅಂಗವೇ ಚುನಾವಣೆ. ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಿರುವುದೇ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಚಲನಶೀಲತೆಯನ್ನು ಕಾಪಾಡುವ ಮಹತ್ಕಾರ್ಯ ಈಡೇರಿಸಲು. ಈ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಕಾಪಾಡದೇ ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ಆಪ್ತಿಕೊಂಡರೆ, ಧರ್ಮವು ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಬದಿಗೆ ಸರಿಸಿ ಮುನ್ನೆಲೆಗೆ ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದರಿಂದ ಪ್ರಜಾತಂತ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ಧಕ್ಕೆ ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಆಗ ಪ್ರಜಾತಂತ್ರದ ಅವಿಭಾಜ್ಯ ಅಂಗವಾದ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೂ ಉಳಿಗಾಲವಿಲ್ಲದಂತಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವ ಮತ್ತು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯ: ಒಂದು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮುನ್ನುಡಿ:

ಪ್ರಪಂಚದ ಎಲ್ಲ ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಧರ್ಮಗಳಿವೆ. ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕವಾಗಿ ಒಂದು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಧರ್ಮಗಳು ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಂಡಿವೆ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಪಾಲುದಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಅನುಭವಿಸಿವೆ. ಪ್ರಪಂಚದ ಎಲ್ಲ ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಒಂದು ಅಥವಾ ಎರಡು ಧರ್ಮಗಳಿವೆ. ಆದರೆ ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಪಂಚದ ಉಳಿದೆಲ್ಲ ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಧರ್ಮಗಳಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಕಾಣುತ್ತೇವೆ. ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ರಾಜಕೀಯವನ್ನು ಧರ್ಮದಿಂದ ಬೇರ್ಪಡಿಸಿ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡುವುದು ಕಷ್ಟ ಎನ್ನುವಷ್ಟರ ಮಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಪರಸ್ಪರ ನಂಟು ಹೊಂದಿವೆ. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿನ ಬಹುತೇಕ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸಾಮ್ರಾಟರು ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನೇ ತಮ್ಮ ರಾಜನೀತಿಯ ಮೂಲವಾಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಆಳ್ವಿಕೆ ನಡೆಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಈ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಭಾರತ ದೇಶಕ್ಕೆ 1947 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಬ್ರಿಟೀಷರಿಂದ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ದೊರೆಯಿತು. 1950 ಜನವರಿ 26 ರಂದು ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ತತ್ವವನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಮಹತ್ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಹೊಂದಿರುವ “ಭಾರತದ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ” ಜಾರಿಗೆ ಬಂದಿತು. ತನ್ಮೂಲಕ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಜೀವವನ್ನು ಉಳಿಸಿ

ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಚೈತನ್ಯಶೀಲತೆಯನ್ನು ಕಾಪಾಡುವ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯೂ ಜಾರಿಗೆ ಬಂದಿತು. ಈ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯು ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳ ನೆಲೆಗಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಯಬೇಕಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಜನರಲ್ಲಿ ಬೇರೂರಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಜನಕಲ್ಯಾಣ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಪೂರೈಸುವ ಆಸ್ವಾಸನೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡುವ ಮತ್ತು ಗೆದ್ದ ನಂತರ ನೀಡಿದ ಆಸ್ವಾಸನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಈಡೇರಿಸುವ ಕಾರ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ತೊಡಗಬೇಕಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಆದರೆ ನಮ್ಮ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಧಾರಿತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಮುಂಚೆ ಆಚರಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿದ್ದ ಊಳಿಗಮಾನ್ಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಪ್ರಧಾನ ಅಂಗವಾಗಿದ್ದ ದರ್ಮವನ್ನು ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಸುವುದು ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆ ಪಡೆಯಿತು. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನೇ ನೆಲೆಯಾಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಗೆದ್ದು ದೇಶವನ್ನು ಆಳುವುದು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಸಂಗತಿಯಾಗಿ ಬೆಳೆಯಿತು. ದಾರ್ಮಿಕ ನೆಲೆ ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಇಂದು ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿನ ಪ್ರಬಲ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳಾಗಿ ಬೆಳೆದಿವೆ. ಇಂತಹ ಕಾಲಘಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ದೇಶದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಸ್ಥಾನ ಪಡೆದ ನಂತರದ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಗಳು, ಇದರಿಂದಂಟಾಗುವ ಸಾಧಕ ಬಾಧಕಗಳು, ದೇಶದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಜಾತಂತ್ರ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಮೇಲಾಗುವ ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳು; ಜನಜೀವನ, ಜೀವನ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳು, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ-ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ವಿಚಾರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಉಂಟಾಗುವ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗಳು, ಪ್ರಜಾತಂತ್ರ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿನ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಪಾವಿತ್ರತೆಯನ್ನು ಕಾಪಾಡಲು ಇರುವ ಪರಿಹಾರೋಪಾಯಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ಒಂದು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಇದಾಗಿದೆ.

ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿನ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಧರ್ಮಗಳ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆ:

ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮವು ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆದಿದೆ. ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವವನ್ನು ಧರ್ಮವು ಪ್ರಭಾವಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಲವು ಧರ್ಮಗಳಿವೆ. ಈ ಧರ್ಮಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಅಪಾರ ನಂಬಿಕೆ ಇದೆ. ಈ ನಂಬಿಕೆಗಳು ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಮೇಲೆ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುತ್ತವೆ. ಇಂತಹ ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವಿಧ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಧನಾತ್ಮಕವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಋಣಾತ್ಮಕವಾಗಿ ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ಬಳಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಜನರ ಬೆಂಬಲ ಪಡೆಯುವ ಏಕೈಕ ಅಸ್ತವಾಗಿ ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ಬಳಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸೋಲುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ಗೆಲ್ಲುವಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮವು ಬಹು ಮುಖ್ಯ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸಿದೆ. ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ವಿಷಯಗಳನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಕೂಡ ಧರ್ಮವು ಬಹುಮುಖ್ಯ ಪಾತ್ರ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಿದೆ.

ಭರತ ಖಂಡದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಹುಮುಖ್ಯ ಧರ್ಮಗಳು ಜನ್ಮತಳೆದಿವೆ. ಕ್ರಿ.ಪೂ. 6 ನೇ ಶತಮಾನಕ್ಕಿಂತಲೂ ಮುಂಚೆ ಹಿಂದೂ ಧರ್ಮವು ಜನ್ಮ ತಳೆದು ಬೆಳೆಯಿತು. ಕ್ರಿ.ಪೂ. 6 ನೇ ಶತಮಾನದ ನಂತರ ಬೌದ್ಧ ಧರ್ಮವು ಜನ್ಮ ತಳೆಯಿತು. ಇವೆರಡೂ ಧರ್ಮಗಳು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ-ರಾಜಕೀಯ-ಆರ್ಥಿಕವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆದಿದ್ದವು. ಹಿಂದೂ ಧರ್ಮವು ವೇದಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ತನ್ನ ನೆಲೆ ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಈ ಧರ್ಮದ ಹಲವು ನಂಬಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಆಚರಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮವೂ ಒಂದು. ಹಿಂದೂ ಧರ್ಮದ ವೇದಗಳ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಧರ್ಮವೆಂದರೆ, ಒಳ್ಳೆಯದನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಸರಿಯಾಗಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಮಾಡುವುದು ಎಂದರ್ಥ. ಬುದ್ಧನಿಂದ ಪ್ರಾರಂಭಗೊಂಡ ಬೌದ್ಧ ಧರ್ಮವು ಆಚರಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿದ್ದು

ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನಿಯಮಗಳ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಪ್ರತಿಭಟಿಸಿ ಪ್ರಗತಿಪರ ಎನಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಬೆಳೆಯಿತು. ಮಾನವರ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಕಷ್ಟ ಕೋಟಲೆಗಳನ್ನು ದೂರ ಮಾಡಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ಬೋಧಿಸಿತು.

ಮೌರ್ಯ ಸಾಮ್ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಮಹಾನ್ ನಾಯಕ ಅಶೋಕ ಚಕ್ರವರ್ತಿಯು ಬೌದ್ಧಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ಸ್ವೀಕರಿಸಿದನು ಮತ್ತು ಪರಧರ್ಮ ಸಹಿಷ್ಣುತೆಯನ್ನು ಬೋಧಿಸಿದನು, ಆತನ ನಂತರ ಪ್ರಬಲ ಗುಪ್ತ ಮತ್ತು ಚೋಳರು ಹಿಂದೂ ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸಿದರು. ಕ್ರಿ.ಶ. 7ನೇ ಶತಮಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ಹೊಸ ಧರ್ಮ ಇಸ್ಲಾಂನ ಪರಿಚಯವಾಯಿತು. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಹೊಸ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಯು ನಿರ್ಮಾಣಗೊಂಡಿತು. ಭಾರತದ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಇಸ್ಲಾಂ ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಬಲವಾಗಿ ಬೆಳೆಸಿದವರಲ್ಲಿ ದೆಹಲಿ ಸುಲ್ತಾನರು ಮತ್ತು ಮೊಘಲರು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರವಹಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಮೊಘಲರ ದೊರೆ ಅಕ್ಬರ್ ವಿವಿಧ ಧರ್ಮಗಳ ಸಾಮರಸ್ಯದ ಬೋಧನೆ ಮಾಡಲು ದೀನ್-ಇ-ಇಲಾಹಿಯನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಿದನು. ಅಕ್ಬರನ ನಂತರದ ದೊರೆಗಳು ಹಿಂದೂ ರಾಜರೊಡನೆ ಘರ್ಷಣೆಗಳಿಂದ ಕಾರಣದಿಂದಾಗಿ ಬಿಕ್ಕಟ್ಟಿನ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿ ಉಂಟಾಗಿದ್ದು ಈಗ ಇತಿಹಾಸ.

17 ನೇ ಶತಮಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಯುರೋಪಿಯನ್ನರು ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ಬಂದು ಕ್ರಿಶ್ಚಿಯನ್ ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ಪರಿಚಯಿಸಿದರು. ಜೊತೆ-ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಪಾಶ್ಚಿಮಾತ್ಯ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ , ಸಮಾನತೆ ,ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ, ಭ್ರಾತೃತ್ವ ದಂತಹ ಪಾಶ್ಚಿಮಾತ್ಯ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಕೂಡ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ಪರಿಚಯಿಸಿದರು. ತಮ್ಮ ಒಡೆದು ಆಳುವ ನೀತಿಯ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿ 1905 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಲಾರ್ಡ್ ಕರ್ಜನ್ ನೇತೃತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಂಗಾಳವನ್ನು ಧರ್ಮದ ಆಧಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಭಜನೆಗೊಳಿಸಿದರು. 1909 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಮಿಂಟೋ-ಮಾರ್ಲೆ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳ ಹೆಸರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಆಧಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಆರಂಭಿಸಿದರು. ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ ಧರ್ಮದ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಪರಿಚಯಿಸಿದರು. ಇದರ ಪರಿಣಾಮವಾಗಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ಥಿತೆಯ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯು ತೀವ್ರ ಸ್ವರೂಪವನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡಿತು. ಒಂದೆಡೆ ಸಾವರ್ಕರ್, ಗೋಳವಲ್ಕರ್, ಹೆಡಗೆವಾರ್ ಹಿಂದೂ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ಥಿತೆಯನ್ನು ಭಾರತೀಯ ಹಿಂದೂಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಬೆಳೆಸಲು ಆರಂಭಿಸಿದರು. ಮಹಮ್ಮದ್ ಇಕ್ಬಾಲ್ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಮ್ಮದ್ ಅಲಿ ಜಿನ್ನಾರವರು ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ಥಿತೆಯನ್ನು ಭಾರತೀಯ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂಮರಲ್ಲಿ ಬೆಳೆಸಲು ಆರಂಭಿಸಿದರು.

ಸರ್ವೇಜನಾಃ ಸುಖಿನೋ ಭವಂತು

ಹಿಂದೂ ಧರ್ಮದ ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆ ಪಡೆದಿರುವ ಶ್ಲೋಕವಾಗಿದೆ. ಸರ್ವ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಒಳಿತಾಗಬೇಕೆಂಬುದೇ ಇದರ ಆಶಯ. ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮವು ಸರ್ವರಿಗೆ ಒಳಿತನ್ನು ಬಯಸುವಂತೆ ಮಾರ್ಗದರ್ಶನ ನೀಡುವ ನೀತಿಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವಾಗಿ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡಿದೆ ಎಂಬ ವಿಷಯ ತಿಳಿಯುತ್ತದೆ.

ಧರ್ಮವು ಜನರನ್ನು ಒಂದಾಗಿಸುವ ಪ್ರತಿಪರ ಕಾರ್ಯದ ರೂವಾರಿ.

ಭಾರತ ಉಪಖಂಡದಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಜೀವನದ ಶ್ರೇಷ್ಠ ಮೌಲ್ಯವನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸಿದ ಮೊದಲ ಧರ್ಮವೇ ಹಿಂದೂ ಧರ್ಮ. (ನಂತರದ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಗಾಮಿಯಾಯಿತು). ಆನಂತರ ಬೌದ್ಧ ಮತ್ತು ಜೈನ ಧರ್ಮ ಈ ಕಾರ್ಯ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸಿದವು. ಮಧ್ಯಪ್ರಾಚ್ಯ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳ ಮರುಭೂಮಿ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದ ಬುಡಕಟ್ಟು ಜನರ ಆಂತರಿಕ ಕಲಹಗಳಿಗೆ ಇತಿಶ್ರೀ ಹಾಡಿ

ಉನ್ನತ ಜೀವನದ ಆದರ್ಶಗಳನ್ನು ಬೋಧನೆ ಮಾಡಿದ ಮೊಹಮ್ಮದ್ ಪೈಗಂಬರ್ ಇಸ್ಲಾಂ ಧರ್ಮದ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಕಾರಣರಾದರು. ಯೇಸು ಕ್ರಿಸ್ತನು ಕ್ರೈಸ್ತ ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ಹುಟ್ಟು ಹಾಕಿದನು. ಆ ಕಾಲದ ಉನ್ನತ ವಿಚಾರ ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದ ಈ ಎಲ್ಲ ಧರ್ಮಗಳು ಆ ಕಾಲದ ಜನರನ್ನು ಒಂದುಗೂಡಿಸಿದ್ದವು. ಒಂದು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಆಚರಣೆ, ಒಂದು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ದೇವರ ಪೂಜೆ ಹೀಗೆ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಅವರದೇ ಆದ ಒಂದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದರು.

ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು

ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳೇ ಪ್ರಭುಗಳೆಂದು ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸುವ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯೇ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆ. ಈ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯು ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳಿಂದಲೇ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕಾರ್ಯಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರತ್ಯಕ್ಷವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪರೋಕ್ಷವಾಗಿ ಜನರು ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಚಲಾಯಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಈ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ತಮ್ಮ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಚಲಾಯಿಸಲು ತಮ್ಮ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳನ್ನು ಆಡಳಿತ ಸ್ಥಾನಕ್ಕೆ ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡುವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯೇ ಚುನಾವಣೆ. ಚುನಾವಣೆಯು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಆತ್ಮ ಮತ್ತು ಹೃದಯ ದಂತೆ ಕೆಲಸ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಹಬ್ಬ ಎಂದೂ ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಚುನಾವಣೆ ಇಲ್ಲದ ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಊಹಿಸುವುದೇ ಕಷ್ಟ.

ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿತ್ವದ ಉಸಿರು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯ

ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮಾನತೆ, ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ, ಭ್ರಾತೃತ್ವ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಗಳು ಮಹತ್ವ ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡಿವೆ. ಈ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಸಾಕಾರಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ವರಿಗೂ ಸರಿ ಕಾಣಿಸುವ ತಮ್ಮ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಗಳನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡುವುದು ಮಹತ್ವದ ಅಂಶವಾಗಿದೆ. ತಮ್ಮ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಯು ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ನಡೆಸದೇ ಹೋದರೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಯನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ಈ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಿಂದ ದೊರೆಯುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯಕ್ಕೆ ಮಹತ್ವ ಬರುವುದು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಿಂದ ಎಂಬ ಅಂಶ ಗುರುತರವಾದದ್ದು.

ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ನೈಜ ಪಾತ್ರ.

ಸಮಾನತೆ, ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ, ಭ್ರಾತೃತ್ವ ಘೋಷಣೆಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ 1789 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಫ್ರೆಂಚ್ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಕ್ರಾಂತಿ ನೆರವೇರಿತು. ಸಮಾನತೆ, ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಹೋದರತೆಯೆಂಬ ಉದಾತ್ತ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಈ ಕ್ರಾಂತಿ ಜನ್ಮ ನೀಡಿತು. ಜಗತ್ತಿನ ಬಹುತೇಕ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಮೌಲ್ಯಧಾರಿತ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯು ಜಾರಿಗೆ ಬಂದಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಜೆಗಳು ಪ್ರಭುಗಳಾಗಿ ಆಳ್ವಿಕೆ ನಡೆಸಲು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲಾಯಿತು. ಈ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಸಾಕಾರಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಜನರ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಬಗೆಹರಿಸಲು, ಜನರಿಗೆ ಸುಖಕರ ಜೀವನವನ್ನು ಖಾತ್ರಿಪಡಿಸಲು, ಕಲ್ಯಾಣರಾಜ್ಯ ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಪಡುತ್ತೇವೆಂದು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸಬೇಕು ಮತ್ತು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಗೆದ್ದ ನಂತರ ತಮ್ಮ ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದನೆಗಾಗಿ ಶ್ರಮಿಸಬೇಕು.

'ರಾಜಕೀಯ' ಮತ್ತು 'ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯ'ದ ನಡುವಿನ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸ

ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ಮನುಷ್ಯನು ಸಂಘಜೀವಿಯಾಗಿ ಜೀವನ ನಡೆಸಲು ತೊಡಗಿದಾಗಿನಿಂದಲೂ ಇದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯವು ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಪ್ರತಿಫಲವಾಗಿದೆ.

ರಾಜರ ಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದಲ್ಲಾಗಲಿ, ಗುಲಾಮಗಿರಿ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಾಗಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೋಡಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಿಲ್ಲ.

ಭಾರತದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯಕ್ಕೆ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ದೊರೆತ ಪ್ರೇರಣೆಗಳು.

ಲಾರ್ಡ್ ಕರ್ಜನ್ 1905ನೇ ಇಸವಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮದ ಆಧಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಂಗಾಳವನ್ನು ವಿಭಜನೆ ಮಾಡಿದನು. 1909 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ ಸಮುದಾಯಕ್ಕೆ ಧರ್ಮಾಧಾರಿತ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಾತಿನಿಧ್ಯ ದೊರಕಿತು. ಸಾವರ್ಕರ್, ಗೋಳವಲ್ಕರ್, ಹೆಡಗೆವಾರ್ ಹಿಂದುತ್ವ ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತವನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಹಿಂದೂ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾದವನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸಿದರು. ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಪ್ರತಿಯಾಗಿ ಮಹಮ್ಮದ್ ಇಕ್ಬಾಲ್, ಮಹಮ್ಮದ್ ಅಲಿ ಜಿನ್ನಾ, ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರವಾದವನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸಿದರು. ಇನ್ನೊಂದೆಡೆ ಕೈಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆ, ಬಾಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹರೇ ರಾಮ್ ಮಂತ್ರ ಜಪಿಸುತ್ತಾ ಹಿಂದೂ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ ಭೇದ ಭಾವ ಮಾಡಬಾರದೆಂದು ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸಿದ ಮಹಾತ್ಮಾ ಗಾಂಧಿಜಿಯವರ ದ್ವಂದ್ವ ನೀತಿ. 1947 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮದ ಆಧಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ದೇಶ ವಿಭಜನೆ ಯಾದ ಘಟನೆ. ಈ ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕ ಘಟನೆಗಳಿಂದ ಪಾರ ಕಲಿತ ನಾಯಕರು ಭಾರತದಂತಹ ಬೃಹತ್ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಒಡೆದು ಆಳುವ ನೀತಿಯನ್ನು ಸಾಕಾರಗೊಳಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದರೆ ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ಆಶ್ರಯಿಸಬೇಕೆಂಬುದನ್ನು ಅರಿತು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮದ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಧಾರಾಳವಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಲು ಆರಂಭಿಸಿದರು.

ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗಳು

1980 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ವಾಪನೆಗೊಂಡ ಬಿಜೆಪಿಯು ಹಿಂದೂ ಧರ್ಮ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಮಜನ್ಮಭೂಮಿ ವಿಷಯಗಳಿಂದಾಗಿಯೇ ಇಂದು ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಬಲ ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷವಾಗಿ ಬೆಳೆದಿದೆ. 1980 ರಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಮಜನ್ಮಭೂಮಿ ವಿವಾದ ಆರಂಭವಾದಾಗ ಬಹುಸಂಖ್ಯಾತ ಹಿಂದೂ ಜನರ ಬೆಂಬಲ ಪಡೆಯಲು ಅಂದಿನ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಎರಡು ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ಪೈಪೋಟಿ ನಡೆಯಿತು. 1985 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಶ್ರೀ ರಾಜೀವ್ ಗಾಂಧಿ ನೇತೃತ್ವದ ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಪಕ್ಷವು ವಿವಾದಿತ ರಾಮಜನ್ಮಭೂಮಿ ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ಹಿಂದಿನ ಗೇಟ್ಸ್ ಬೀಗ ತೆರೆಸಿ ಪೂಜೆ ನೆರವೇರಿಸಲು ಅನುಮತಿ ನೀಡಲಾಯಿತು.

2002 ರ ಗುಜರಾತಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಗೋಧ್ರಾ ಹತ್ಯಾಕಾಂಡದ ನಂತರ ಸತತವಾಗಿ ಆ ಪ್ರದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಿಜೆಪಿ ಪಕ್ಷವು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜಯ ಸಾಧಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಬಂದಿದೆ.

ಹಿಂದೂ, ಹಿಂದಿ, ಹಿಂದೂಸ್ತಾನ್ ಘೋಷಣೆಯೂ ಕೂಡ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಬಲ ಅಜಂಡಾ ಆಗಿ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರತಿಫಲ ನೀಡಿದೆ.

ವಿಶ್ವದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಧರ್ಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವ ಮತ್ತು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗಳು.

ಜರ್ಮನಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅಡಾಲ್ಫ್ ಹಿಟ್ಲರ್ ಮತ್ತು ಇಟಲಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಜಿನೆಟೋ ಮುಸ್ಸೋಲಿನಿ 1925-1944 ರ ಅವಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮೊದಲ ಮಹಾಯುದ್ಧದ ಸೋಲಿನಿಂದ ಹತಾಶರಾಗಿದ್ದ ಜರ್ಮನ್ ಮತ್ತು ಇಟಲಿಯ ಜನರಿಗೆ ತಮ್ಮ ಸೋಲಿಗೆ ಯಹೂದಿಗಳ ಕಾರಣ ಹಾಗೂ ಪ್ರಬಲವಾದ ದೇಶ ಕಟ್ಟಲು ಯಹೂದಿಗಳು ಅಡೆತಡೆಯಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆಂದು ನಂಬುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜಯಗಳಿಸಿ ಸರ್ವಾಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳಾಗಿ ಮೆರೆದರು.

ಅಮೇರಿಕಾ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ 19 ಮತ್ತು 20 ನೇ ಶತಮಾನದ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಮೇರಿಕಾದ ಉತ್ತರ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಹುತೇಕ ಪ್ರೊಟೆಸ್ಟಂಟ್ ಪಂಗಡದ ಜನರು ರಿಪಬ್ಲಿಕನ್ ಮತ್ತು ಬಹುತೇಕ ಕ್ಲಾಥೋಲಿಕ್ ಪಂಗಡದವರು ಡೆಮೋಕ್ರಾಟ್ ರಿಗೆ ಬೆಂಬಲ ನೀಡಿರುವುದು ಸಾಬೀತಾಗಿದೆ. ಅಮೇರಿಕಾದ ದಕ್ಷಿಣ ಭಾಗದಲ್ಲಿ 1860-1960 ರ ಅವಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಬಹುತೇಕ ಬಿಳಿಯರು ಡೆಮೋಕ್ರಾಟರಿಗೆ ಮತ್ತು ಬಹುತೇಕ ಕರಿಯರು ರಿಪಬ್ಲಿಕನ್ ಪಕ್ಷಕ್ಕೆ ಬೆಂಬಲ ನೀಡಿರುವುದು ಕಂಡುಬಂದಿದೆ. ಅಮೇರಿಕಾದಲ್ಲಿನ 65% ಜನಸಂಖ್ಯೆ (2019 ರವರೆಗೆ) ಕ್ರಿಶ್ಚಿಯನ್ನರಿಂದ ಉಳಿದ ಜನಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯು ಹಿಂದೂ, ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ, ಯಹೂದಿ ಮತ್ತು ಇನ್ನುಳಿದ ಧರ್ಮಗಳಿಂದ ಕೂಡಿದೆ.

ಶ್ರೀಲಂಕಾ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಬೌದ್ಧ ಧರ್ಮವು ಜನರನ್ನು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ದ್ರವೀಕರಣಗೊಳಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಬಲ ಪಾತ್ರ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಇಸ್ಲಂ ಧರ್ಮವು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜನರನ್ನು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕವಾಗಿ ದ್ರವೀಕರಣಗೊಳಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

“ಜಪಾನ್ ದೇಶದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾವೊಂದು ಧರ್ಮದ ಪ್ರಾಬಲ್ಯ ಕಂಡುಬರುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಜಪಾನ್ ದೇಶದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮವು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಜನರು ತಮ್ಮ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ಥಿತೆಯ ಆಧಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ ಚಲಾಯಿಸುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಜನರು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ದ್ರವೀಕರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಒಳಗಾಗುವುದುಲ್ಲ”ವೆಂದು ಆಕ್ಸೆಲ್ ಕ್ಲೈನ್ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ಟೀವನ್ ಆರ್. ರೀಡ್ ಅವರು ಇನ್ವಿಟ್ಯೂಟ್ ಆಫ್ ಈಸ್ಟ್ ಏಷಿಯನ್ ಸ್ಟಡೀಸ್, ಯುನಿವರ್ಸಿಟಿ ಆಫ್ ಕ್ಯಾಲಿಫೋರ್ನಿಯಾ, ಬರ್ಕಲಿ (ISBN-13:978-1-55729-162-2(electronic) ISBN-13:978-1-55729-111-0(print) ISBN-10:1-55729-111-X (Print) ಪುಟಸಂಖ್ಯೆ 25.) ಇವರು ಪ್ರಕಟಿಸಿರುವ ಜರ್ನಲ್ನಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಕಟವಾಗಿರುವ ಸಂಶೋಧನಾ ಲೇಖನದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ಥಿತೆಯನ್ನು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದರ ಹಿಂದಿರುವ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳು

ಒಂದು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಧರ್ಮಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿದ ಜನರು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಒಂದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ಭಾಷೆ, ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ, ಆಚರಣೆ, ನಂಬಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. (ಭಾರತದಂತಹ ವಿಶಾಲ ಮತ್ತು ವೈವಿಧ್ಯತೆಯಿಂದ ಕೂಡಿದ ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾತ್ರ ಒಂದೇ ಧರ್ಮದ ಜನರ ವಿವಿಧ ಭಾಷೆಗಳು ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತವೆ.) ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ನಂಬಿಕೆಗಳ ಆಧಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಾಗಿರುವ ಮತ್ತು ಜೀವನದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಆಯಾಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಮ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಜನರನ್ನು ಪುನಃ ಒಂದೂಗೊಡಿಸುವುದು ಸಂಕಷ್ಟದ ಕಾರ್ಯವಲ್ಲ. ಆ ಧರ್ಮದ ಜನರ ಪರವಾಗಿ ಮಾತನಾಡಿ ಅವರ ಓಲೈಕೆಗಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸಿದರೆ ಸಾಕು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಮತಗಳ ದ್ರವೀಕರಣ ಸುಲಭಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ. ಧನಾತ್ಮಕ ಆಯಾಮದಲ್ಲಿ ನೋಡಿದಾಗ ಈ ಅಂಶವು ತಿಳಿಯುತ್ತದೆ. ಇನ್ನು ಋಣಾತ್ಮಕ ಆಯಾಮದಲ್ಲಿ ನೋಡುವುದಾದರೆ ಒಂದು ಧರ್ಮದ ಜನರನ್ನು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಮತ ದ್ರವೀಕರಣಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಇನ್ನೊಂದು ಧರ್ಮದ ಜನರ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಮಾತನಾಡಿ ಅವರನ್ನು ಅಪರಾಧಿಗಳಂತೆ ಬಿಂಬಿಸಿದರೆ ಸಾಕು.

ವಿಶ್ವಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಮತ್ತು ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಇಂದಿನ ಆಳುವ ವರ್ಗವು ದೇಶದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಜನರನ್ನು ಆರ್ಥಿಕವಾಗಿ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕವಾಗಿ, ರಾಜಕೀಯವಾಗಿ ಸಬಲಗೊಳಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ

ವಿಫಲವಾಗುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಎಷ್ಟೇ ಅಂದ ಚಂದದ, ಬಣ್ಣ-ಬಣ್ಣದ ಹೆಸರುಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊತ್ತ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನೀತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಿದರೂ ಕೂಡ, ಜನರ ನೈಜ ಆರ್ಥಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ. ಈ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಿಂದಾಗಿ ಜನರು ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಅಸಮಾಧಾನ ಹೊಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇದನ್ನು ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ ಅರ್ಥೈಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದ ಆಳ್ವಿಕೆ ವರ್ಗವು ಜನರು ಹೊಸ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಹುಡುಕಾಟದಲ್ಲಿ ತೊಡಗುವುದನ್ನು ತಡೆಯಲು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಮುನ್ನೆಲೆಗೆ ತಂದು ಆಳ್ವಿಕೆ ನಡೆಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಹೇಗೆ?

ಬಹುಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಜನರ ಬಳಿ ಮತ ಕೇಳುವುದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ, ಜನರಿಗೆ ತಮ್ಮ ಧೈಯೋದ್ದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಚಾರಪಡಿಸುವ ಸಲುವಾಗಿ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಣಾಳಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊರಡಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಭಾಷಣಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಕರಪತ್ರ, ಗೋಡೆಬರಹ, ಜಾಹೀರಾತು, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳನ್ನು ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಪ್ರಚಾರ ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತವೆ. ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ವಿಷಯಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಣಾಳಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಬಹಿರಂಗ ಪ್ರಚಾರ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳು ನಡೆಯಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವೇ ಇಲ್ಲ ಎನ್ನುವಷ್ಟರಮಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗಾಗಿ ಭಾರತದ ವಿವಿಧ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಣಾಳಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೋಡೋಣ.

2024 ರ ಭಾರತದ ಸಾರ್ವತ್ರಿಕ ಲೋಕಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯ ಭಿಜೆಪಿಯ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಣಾಳಿಕೆಯ ಇಂಗ್ಲಿಷ್ ಆವೃತ್ತಿಯ ಪುಟ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ 37 ರಲ್ಲಿ ನಮೂದಾಗಿರುವ ಅಂಶ ಹೀಗಿದೆ.

Preserving and promoting the legacy of lord Ram

Ramayana is celebrated across the world, particularly in south and south-east Asia. We will launch a global outreach programme for documenting and promoting the tangible and intangible legacy of lord Ram in all countries. We will celebrate Ramayana Utsava with great fervour across the globe to commemorate the Prana Pratishtha of Ram Lalla.

ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಪಕ್ಷದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಣಾಳಿಕೆಯ ಇಂಗ್ಲಿಷ್ ಆವೃತ್ತಿಯ ಪುಟ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ 7 ರಲ್ಲಿ ನಮೂದಾಗಿರುವ ಅಂಶ ಹೀಗಿದೆ. (ಈ ಅಂಶವು ನಮ್ಮ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಇದೆ, ಆದರೂ ಕೂಡ ಪಕ್ಷದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಣಾಳಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ನಮೂದಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದರೆ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮತಗಳ ಧೃವೀಕರಣಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನವೆಂದು ಕರೆಯಬಹುದು ಮತ್ತು 2014-2024 ರವರೆಗೆ ಬಿಜೆಪಿ ಆಳ್ವಿಕೆ ಅವಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆದ ಹಿಂದೂ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಧೃವೀಕರಣ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆ ಮತ್ತು ಪರಮತ ಅಸಹಿಷ್ಣುತೆಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಹಲವು ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಾಗಿ ಈ ಅಂಶವನ್ನು ಕಾಂಗ್ರೆಸ್ ಪಕ್ಷ ಸೇರಿಸಿದೆ.)

Religious and linguistic minorities

The plurality of religions represents the history of india. History can not be altered. All people living in india and all children born in india are equally entitled to enjoy human rights that includes the right to practis one's religion. Pluralism and diversity constitute the ethos of India and are enshrined in the

Preamble to the constitution of India. Given the history and the democratic traditions of India, the Congress believes that there is no place for authoritarianism or majoritarianism.

Linguistic and religious minorities are granted human and civic rights under the constitution of India. Congress pledges to uphold and protect these rights.

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ವಿಧಾನಸಭಾ ಚುನಾವಣೆ-2023 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಜಿಡಿಎಸ್ ಪಕ್ಷದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಪ್ರಳಾಳಿಕೆಯ ಪುಟ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ 8 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಹೀಗೆ ನಮೂದಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. “ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರ ಏಳಿಗೆ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯ ಮತ್ತು ಮೀಸಲಾತಿ”.

ಈ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ನಾವು ಗಮನವಿಟ್ಟು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡರೆ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ಥಿತಿಯೂ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಎಷ್ಟು ಪ್ರಬಲ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಹೊಂದಿದೆಯೆಂದು ತಿಳಿದುಬರುತ್ತದೆ.

ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮುಖಂಡರು ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನಾಯಕರ ಅಪವಿತ್ರ ಮೈತ್ರಿ.

ಭಾರತ ದೇಶವು ಸಾಧು-ಸಂತರ ನಾಡೆಂದು ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧಿ ಪಡೆದಿದೆ. ಅನಾದಿ ಕಾಲದಿಂದಲೂ ಸಾಧು-ಸಂತರಿಗೆ, ಋಷಿ ಮುನಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಈ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಗ್ರಮಾನ್ಯ ಗೌರವ, ಪ್ರೀತ್ಯಾದರ, ಭಕ್ತಿ ಸಮರ್ಪಣೆ ದೊರೆತಿದೆ. ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಸಂಖ್ಯಾತ ಮಠ-ಮಾನ್ಯಗಳಿವೆ, ಮಸೀದಿ-ಮಂದಿರಗಳಿವೆ, ಚರ್ಚ್, ಸ್ತೂಪಗಳಿವೆ. ಈ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮುಖಂಡರಿಗೆ ಧರ್ಮದ ಕಾರಣದಿಂದಾಗಿ ಜನರು ಅಪಾರ ಭಕ್ತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಗೌರವ ನೀಡುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಆದರೆ ಇದನ್ನು ದುರುಪಯೋಗ ಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿರುವ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮುಖಂಡರು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ಅಪವಿತ್ರ ಮೈತ್ರಿ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡು ಜನರಿಗೆ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಪಕ್ಷವನ್ನು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಬೆಂಬಲಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಕೇಂದ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಆಜ್ಞೆ ಹೊರಡಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕವಾಗಿ ಭಾಷಣಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಪ್ರತಿಯಾಗಿ ಕೋಟ್ಯಂತರ ರೂಪಾಯಿ ಧನಸಹಾಯವನ್ನು ಕೂಡ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳಿಂದ ತಮ್ಮ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಿಗಾಗಿ ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮುಖಂಡರು ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ನಾಯಕರು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಾಗಿ ಪರಸ್ಪರ ಕೊಡುಕೊಳ್ಳುವಲ್ಲಿ ತನ್ಮಯರಾಗಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಜನರ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಭಕ್ತಿಗೆ ತಿಲಾಂಜಲಿ ಒಂದೆಡೆಯಾದರೆ, ಜನರ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಹಕ್ಕಿಗೆ ತಿಲಾಂಜಲಿ ಇನ್ನೊಂದೆಡೆ ನಡೆಯುತ್ತದೆ.

ಮತಭ್ರಾಂಕ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಕೋಮು ಧ್ರುವೀಕರಣದ ಕೆಲವು ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗಳು.

ಪೌರತ್ವ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ-2019 ನ್ನು ಸಂಸತ್ತು 11 ಡಿಸೆಂಬರ್ 2019 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಅಂಗೀಕಾರಗೊಳಿಸಿತು. 2014 ಡಿಸೆಂಬರ್ 31 ಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಮೊದಲು ಭಾರತ ದೇಶಕ್ಕೆ ಆಫಘಾನಿಸ್ತಾನ, ಬಾಂಗ್ಲಾದೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ಪಾಕಿಸ್ತಾನದಿಂದ ಭಾರತಕ್ಕೆ ಬಂದು ನೆಲೆಸಿರುವ ಹಿಂದೂ, ಸಿಖ್ಖರು, ಬೌದ್ಧರು, ಜೈನರು, ಪಾರ್ಸಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಕ್ರೈಸ್ತರಿಗೆ ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದ ಪೌರತ್ವ ನೀಡುವ ಉದ್ದೇಶವನ್ನು ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಇದೇ ಅವಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಇದೇ ದೇಶಗಳಿಂದ ವಲಸೆ ಬಂದು ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ನೆಲೆಸಿರುವ ಮುಸ್ಲಿಂ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಭಾರತದ ಪೌರತ್ವ ನೀಡುವ ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಹೊಂದಿಲ್ಲದಿರುವುದು ಪ್ರಶ್ನಾರ್ಹವಾಗಿದೆ. ಮತಭ್ರಾಂಕಾಗಿ ನಡೆಸಿದ ಯಶಸ್ವೀ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಚರಣೆ ಇದಾಗಿದೆ.

ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ವಿವಾದಗ್ರಸ್ತವಾಗಿರುವ ವಕ್ಫ್ ಮಂಡಳಿ ವಿಷಯವೂ ಕೂಡ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಿರುವ ಉಪಚುನಾವಣೆ (2024 ನವೆಂಬರ್) ರಾಜಕೀಯಕ್ಕೆ ಆಹಾರವಾಗಿದೆ. ಎಲ್ಲಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಹಿಂದಿರುವ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಜನರಿಗೆ ತಾವೆಷ್ಟು ಪ್ರಮಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು

ಪ್ರೀತಿಸುತ್ತೇವೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಸಾಬೀತುಪಡಿಸಲು ಹರಸಾಹಸ ಪಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಆದರೆ ತಮ್ಮ ಹಿಂದಿರುವ ಈ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಜನರು ಬೆಳನಷ್ಟ, ಬೆಳೆದ ಬೆಳೆಗೆ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಬೆಲೆ ಇಲ್ಲದಿರುವುದು, ಬೆಲೆ ಏರಿಕೆ, ಆರೋಗ್ಯ-ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದ ವ್ಯಾಪಾರೀಕರಣ, ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಅಧಃಪತನ, ನಿರುದ್ಯೋಗದಂತಹ ಜ್ವಲಂತ ಸಂಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಂದ ತೊಂದರೆಗೆ ಈಡಾಗಿದ್ದರೂ ಈ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಬಗೆಹರಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ತಾವೆಷ್ಟು ಮುಂದು ಎಂದು ಸಾಬೀತು ಪಡಿಸಲು ಯಾವೊಂದು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷವೂ ಮುಂದೆ ಬರದೇ ಇರುವುದು ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ದುರಂತವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇಂದು ಒಂದು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಜನರನ್ನು ಪ್ರೀತಿಸಿ, ನಿಮಗಾಗಿ ರಕ್ತವನ್ನೇ ಹರಿಸುತ್ತೇವೆ ಎಂದು ಭಾಷಣ ಮಾಡುವ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ನಡೆಸುವ ಪಕ್ಷದ ಮುಖಂಡರು ದಿಢೀರನೆ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಚುರಪಡಿಸುವ ಪಕ್ಷಕ್ಕೆ ಪಕ್ಷಾಂತರಗೊಂಡು ಅಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಕೂಡ ಸಕ್ರಿಯವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಯಶಸ್ವಿಯಾಗಿ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಮುಂದುವರೆಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಹೋಗುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಎಂತಹ ವಿಪರ್ಯಾಸದ ಸಂಗತಿ. ಇದು ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಮಾರಣಹೋಮವಾಗಿದೆ. ಜನರ ಆಶೋತ್ತರಗಳ ವಿಡಂಬನೆಯಾಗಿದೆ.

ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ಮೇಳೈಸುವುದರಿಂದಾಗುವ ಅಪಾಯಗಳು.

ಕೋಮುವಾದಕ್ಕೆ ರಹದಾರಿ:

ಬಹುಧರ್ಮಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಭಾರತದಂತಹ ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವಗಳನ್ನು ಬಳಸುವುದರಿಂದ ಜನರಲ್ಲಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ನಂಬಿಕೆಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ವಿಶ್ವಾಸ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಧರ್ಮದಿಂದಲೇ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳು ದೊರೆಯುತ್ತವೆ ಎಂಬ ಭಾವ ಮೂಡಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಮುಖಂಡರೊಂದಿಗೆ ಬೆಸೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಸಹಜವಾಗಿಯೇ ಒಂದು ಧರ್ಮ ಧ್ರುವೀಕರಣಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿದ್ದಂತೆ ಇನ್ನೊಂದು ಧರ್ಮ ಮತ್ತೊಂದು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷದೊಡನೆ ಬೆಸೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ. ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಅಧಿಕಾರಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಧರ್ಮ ಶ್ರೇಷ್ಠ ಉಳಿದೆಲ್ಲವೂ ತಮಗಿಂತಲೂ ಕನಿಷ್ಠ ಎಂದು ಸಾಬೀತುಪಡಿಸುವ ಗೋಜಿಗೆ ಹೋಗಿ ಕೋಮು ಘರ್ಷಣೆಗೆ ಇನ್ನೊಂದು ಧರ್ಮಕ್ಕೆ ಪ್ರಚೋದನೆ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಾಗಿ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ನಡೆಯಬೇಕಿದ್ದ ಹಣಾಹಣಿ ಧರ್ಮಗಳ ನಡುವೆ ಆರಂಭಗೊಂಡು ಕೋಮುವಾದಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಪ್ಯಾಸೀವಾದಕ್ಕೆ ಭದ್ರ ಬುನಾದಿ ದೊರೆಯುತ್ತದೆ.

ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಬಳಸಿ ಚುನಾವಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಗೆಲ್ಲುವ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳಿಗೆ ಸುಲಭವಾಗಿ ಬಹುಸಂಖ್ಯಾತ ಧರ್ಮದ ಬೆಂಬಲ ದೊರೆಯುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಬೆಂಬಲವನ್ನೇ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಇನ್ನೊಂದು ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಮೂಲ ಕಾರಣ ಎಂಬಂತೆ ಬಿಂಬಿಸಿ, ಆರ್ಥಿಕ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ, ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಏಕಸ್ವಾಮ್ಯಾಧಿಪತ್ಯ ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಿ ಫ್ಯಾಸೀವಾದದ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾವನೆಯಲ್ಲಿರುವ “ಜಾತ್ಯತೀತ” ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಗೆ ಧಕ್ಕೆ

ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿಸುವುದರಿಂದ ಬಹುಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರ ಧರ್ಮವು ಅಧಿಕಾರದ ಭಾಗವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರ ಧರ್ಮದ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಅಭದ್ರತೆಯ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿ ಎದುರಿಸುವಂತಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಯು ಜಾತ್ಯತೀತ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಗೆ ಧಕ್ಕೆಯುಂಟು ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.

ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳ ಆಶಯಕ್ಕೆ ಕೊಡಲಿಪೆಟ್ಟು

ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 15- ಧರ್ಮ, ಜಾತಿ, ಜನಾಂಗ, ಲಿಂಗ, ಜನ್ಮಸ್ಥಳ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ತಾರತಮ್ಯ ಮಾಡಬಾರದೆಂದು ಹೇಳುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಮುನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಧರ್ಮವು ಅಧಿಕಾರಸ್ಥರಿಗೆ ಹತ್ತಿರವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುತ್ತದೆ. ಸಹಜವಾಗಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ತಾರತಮ್ಯ ಸುಪ್ತವಾಗಿ ನಡೆಯುತ್ತದೆ.

ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 21- ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಜೀವಿಸುವ ಹಕ್ಕನ್ನು ಖಾತ್ರಿ ಪಡಿಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ಹೇಳುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ನೆಲೆಗಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಯುವ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಗಲಭೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸಲು ಕೂಡ ಹಿಂಜರಿಯುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಗಲಭೆಗಳು ನಡೆದಿರುವುದು ಐತಿಹಾಸಿಕವಾಗಿ ರುಜುವಾತಾಗಿದೆ. ಯಾವ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಯೂ ಇಲ್ಲದ ಮತ್ತು ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಗಲಭೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸದೇ ದೂರ ಉಳಿದಿರುವ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಜನರ ಆಸ್ತಿ-ಪಾಸ್ತಿ ಮತ್ತು ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕ ಜೀವನಕ್ಕೆ ಹಾನಿಗಳಾಗಿವೆ. ಇದು ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 21 ರ ಉಲ್ಲಂಘನೆಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನದ ಅನುಚ್ಛೇದ 25-ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯದ ಹಕ್ಕನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದರೆ ರಾಜಕೀಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಬಲವಾಗಿರುವ ಯಾವುದೇ ಒಂದು ಬಹುಸಂಖ್ಯಾತ ಧರ್ಮವು ಒಂದು ದಿನ ತಮ್ಮ (ಅಲ್ಪಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರ) ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯದ ಹಕ್ಕಿಗೆ ತೊಂದರೆಯನ್ನುಂಟು ಮಾಡಬಹುದೆಂಬ ಭಯದಲ್ಲೇ ಮುಂದುವರೆಯಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಬಹುಸಂಖ್ಯಾತರ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ನೆಲೆಗಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಗೇ ಮುಂದಾಗುವ ಆತಂಕ ಧರ್ಮ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕಾರಣದ ಸಮ್ಮೇಳನದಿಂದ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಪಡೆಯುವ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷವೂ ಅಧಿಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಬರಲು ಬೆಂಬಲ ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಪ್ರಬಲ ಧರ್ಮದ ಮುಲಾಜಿಗೆ ಒಳಗಾಗಿ ಆ ಧರ್ಮದ ಅಣತಿಯಂತೆ ವಿವಾದಾತ್ಮಕ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಲು ಸಿದ್ಧಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳು ಚಿಂತಾಜನಕ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಗೆ ತಲುಪುತ್ತವೆ.

ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಹಬ್ಬ ಎಂದು ಕರೆಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಧರ್ಮದ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಯಾವುದೇ ಅಳುಕಿಲ್ಲದೆ ನಡೆಯತೊಡಗಿದ ಮೇಲೆ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳ ಆಧಾರ ಯಾವ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪಕ್ಷಗಳಿಗೂ ಬೇಡವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಅಂತಿಮವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳ ಉಳಿವಿಗಾಗಿ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕ ಜನಾಂದೋಲನ ನಡೆಸುವ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯತೆ ಎದುರಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಜನರ ಒಗ್ಗಟ್ಟು ನಾಶವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಜನರ ನೈಜ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳು ತರೆಮರೆಗೆ ಸರಿಯುತ್ತಿವೆ.

ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ಥಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಆಧಾರವಾಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಿರುವ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ರಾಜಕೀಯದ ವಿಚ್ಛಿದ್ರಕಾರಿ ಮನೋಭಾವನೆಯನ್ನು ತೊಡೆದುಹಾಕಲು ಅನುಸರಿಸಬೇಕಾದ ಮಾರ್ಗೋಪಾಯಗಳು.

- ಶಾಲೆ , ಆಸ್ಪತ್ರೆ, ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಕಛೇರಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ, ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ದಾಖಲೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ನಮೂದಿಸುವುದನ್ನು ಈ ಕ್ಷಣದಿಂದಲೇ ಕೈಬಿಡಲು ಸಾಂವಿಧಾನಿಕ ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿ ತರಬೇಕು.
- ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಅಸ್ಥಿತೆ ಕೇವಲ ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕ ನೆಲೆಗಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಉಳಿಯುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡಲು ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಹಾಕಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.

- ಧರ್ಮ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರತ್ಯೇಕಗೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು. ಧರ್ಮ ಜನರ ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕ ನಂಬಿಕೆಯಾಗಬೇಕು. ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕವಾಗಿ ರಾಜ್ಯಾಂಗವು ಯಾವುದೇ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹ ನೀಡಬಾರದು ಮತ್ತು ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಬಾರದು.
- ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳಾದ ಸಮಾನತೆ, ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ, ಭ್ರಾತೃತ್ವ, ವೈಚಾರಿಕತೆ, ಮಹಿಳಾ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಾನತೆ ಗಳನ್ನು ವ್ಯಾಪಕವಾಗಿ ಜನರಿಗೆ ತಲುಪಿಸಲು ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳು ಜರುಗಬೇಕು.
- ಕಲೆ, ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯ, ಸಿನಿಮಾ, ನಾಟಕಗಳು ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಜನಮಾನಸಕ್ಕೆ ತಲುಪಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಾಮಾಣಿಕ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನ ಮಾಡಬೇಕು.
- ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಮಾಜವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕರಣಗೊಳಿಸಲು ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಇಚ್ಛಾಶಕ್ತಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಬೇಕು.
- ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳನ್ನು ಬಲಪಡಿಸಬೇಕು. ಜನಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ-1951ನ್ನು ಬಲಪಡಿಸಬೇಕು. ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮ, ಜಾತಿ, ಭಾಷೆಯ ಪ್ರಭಾವವನ್ನು ಬಳಕೆ ಮಾಡುವುದನ್ನು ನಿಷೇಧಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಭಾರತದ ಚುನಾವಣಾ ಆಯೋಗ ಸಬಲಗೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.

ಉಪಸಂಹಾರ

ಧರ್ಮವು ಒಂದಾನೊಂದು ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮಾಜದ ಚಲನಶೀಲ ತತ್ವವಾಗಿ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡಿದೆ. ಧರ್ಮದ ಅಪ್ರಸ್ತುತತೆಯನ್ನು ಅರಿತದ್ದರಿಂದಾಗಿಯೇ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಕ್ರಾಂತಿ ನೆರವೇರಿಸುವ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮ ಬೋಧಿಸಿದ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳಿಗಿಂತ ಉನ್ನತ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಎತ್ತಿ ಹಿಡಿಯಲಾಯಿತು. ಧರ್ಮಕ್ಕಿಂತಲೂ ಉನ್ನತ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಭಾರತ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಅವಿಭಾಜ್ಯ ಅಂಗವೇ ಚುನಾವಣೆ. ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳಿರುವುದೇ ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಚಲನಶೀಲತೆಯನ್ನು ಕಾಪಾಡುವ ಮಹತ್ಕಾರ್ಯ ಈಡೇರಿಸಲು. ಈ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗಳು ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಕಾಪಾಡದೇ ಧರ್ಮವನ್ನು ಆಪ್ತಿಕೊಂಡರೆ, ಧರ್ಮವು ಪ್ರಜಾತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಬದಿಗೆ ಸರಿಸಿ ಮುನ್ನೆಲೆಗೆ ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದರಿಂದ ಪ್ರಜಾತಂತ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ಧಕ್ಕೆ ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಆಗ ಪ್ರಜಾತಂತ್ರದ ಅವಿಭಾಜ್ಯ ಅಂಗವಾದ ಚುನಾವಣೆಗೂ ಉಳಿಗಾಲವಿಲ್ಲದಂತಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಗ್ರಂಥಮುಖ-

ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಲೇ-ಪ್ರೊ. ಎನ್. ಹಾಲಪ್ಪ, ಸ್ವರ್ಧಾ ಉನ್ನತಿ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು.

ಅಂತರರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಸಂಬಂಧಗಳು. ಲೇ-ಪ್ರೊ. ಎನ್. ಹಾಲಪ್ಪ, ಸ್ವರ್ಧಾ ಉನ್ನತಿ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು.

ಭಾರತ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರ. ಲೇ-ಡಾ. ಹೆಚ್. ಎಂ. ರಾಜಶೇಖರ.

CAA NRC NPR ಎಂದರೇನು? ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ಮಾಹಿತಿ-ಸಮಗ್ರ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆ. ಲೇ-ದೊಡ್ಡಿಪಾಳ್ಯ ನರಸಿಂಹಮೂರ್ತಿ.

ಪ್ರಕಟಣೆ-ಗೌರಿ ಮೀಡಿಯಾ ಟ್ರಸ್ಟ್.

ಮಾಕ್ಸ್ವೆಲ್ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನದಲ್ಲಿ ಶಹೀದ್-ಏ-ಆಜಂ ಭಗತ್‌ಸಿಂಗ್. ಲೇ-ಪ್ರವಾಶ್ ಫೋರ್ಷ್.

ಕುವೆಂಪು ವಿಚಾರಧಾರೆ (ಸಂಗ್ರಹ-ಸಂಕಲನ) ಲೇ-ಶಿವರಾಮಯ್ಯ.

ಕೇಸರಿ ಭಯೋತ್ಪಾದನೆ. ಲೇ-ಸುರೇಶ್ ಭಟ್ ಬಾಕ್ಸಬೈಲು. ಲಂಕೇಶ್ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ.

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ಭಾರತೀಯ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಚಿಂತನೆಯ ವಿಶ್ವಕೋಶ. ಸಂಪುಟ-೧. ಲೇ. ಒಡೆಯರ್ ಡಿ. ಹೆಗ್ಡೆ. ಲಿಖಿತ್ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನ.

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಪ್ರದೇಶ ಜನತಾದಳ (ಜಾತ್ಯತೀತ) - ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ವಿಧಾನಸಭೆ ಚುನಾವಣೆ, ಮೇ 10 2023. ಜನತಾ ಪ್ರಣಾಳಿಕೆ.

NYAY PATRA- Lok Sabha Elections-2024. INDIAN NATIONAL CONGRESS

BHARATIYA JANATA PARTY Modi ki Guarantee-2024

ಅಂತರ್ಜಾಲ.

ದಿನಪತ್ರಿಕೆಗಳು, ವೃತ್ತಪತ್ರಿಕೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳು ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ.

ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರ ನಿಯಂತ್ರಣ ಮತ್ತು ನೌಕರಶಾಹಿ ವರ್ಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಪಾತ್ರ

ನಾಗನಾಯ್ಕ

ಸಂಶೋಧನಾರ್ಥಿ, ರಾಜ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ವಿಭಾಗ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು.

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ಸಾರಲೇಖ

ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರ ಸೂಚ್ಯಂಕದ ಪ್ರಕಾರ (Corruption Perception Index-CPI) ಭಾರತವು 2023 ರಲ್ಲಿ 180 ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ 93 ನೇ ಸ್ಥಾನದಲ್ಲಿದೆ. ಭಾರತದ ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆ ಸ್ಕೋರ್ 39 ಆಗಿದ್ದರೆ, 2022 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಅದು 40 ಆಗಿತ್ತು. ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತವು ಕಳೆದ ಕೆಲವು ದಶಕಗಳಿಂದ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟವಾಗಿದೆ. ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಇದನ್ನು ತಡೆಯುವ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿದ್ದು, ಈ ಕಾರಣಕ್ಕಾಗಿ 2005 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯನ್ನು (ಆರ್‌ಟಿಐ) ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಿತು. ಅಂದಿನಿಂದ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ವಲಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರ ಕಡಿಮೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಅದೇ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ನೌಕರಶಾಹಿ ವರ್ಗ ಮೊದಲಿಗಿಂತ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಈ ಲೇಖನವು ದೇಶದ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ನಾಗರಿಕರು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಸಕ್ರಿಯವಾಗಿಸಲು ಹಾಗೂ ಆಡಳಿತವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಕ್ರಿಯಾಶೀಲಗೊಳಿಸಲು RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು ಎಂಬ ಸಲಹೆಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದಲ್ಲದೆ ಶಾಸಕಾಂಗ ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯಾಂಗ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸೂಕ್ತ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಕಾಪಾಡಲು ಎದುರಾಗುತ್ತಿರುವ ಆಡಳಿತಾತ್ಮಕ ಸವಾಲುಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ವಿಮರ್ಶಾತ್ಮಕವಾಗಿ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸಲಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ.

ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪದಗಳು: RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆ, ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರ, ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ನೌಕರಶಾಹಿ ವರ್ಗ, ಉತ್ತರದಾಯಿತ್ವ, ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತ, ಸವಾಲುಗಳು, ಅನುಕೂಲಗಳು.

ಪ್ರಸ್ತಾವನೆ

2005 ರಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾರಿಗೆ ಬಂದ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆ (ಆರ್‌ಟಿಐ) ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿನ ಹೆಗ್ಗುರುತಿನ ಶಾಸನವಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಿಂದ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವುದು ಇದರ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶವಾಗಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಸಕ್ರಿಯವಾಗಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಅನುವು ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುತ್ತದೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಕ್ರಮಗಳು ಪರಿಶೀಲನೆಗೆ ಮುಕ್ತವಾಗಿವೆ ಎಂದು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ನಿರ್ಣಾಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರವನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡುವುದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಆಡಳಿತ ವರ್ಗದ ಮೇಲೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರ ನಂಬಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಲಕ್ಷಣಗಳು

RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಇತರೆ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳಿಂದ ಹಲವಾರು ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಲಕ್ಷಣಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ

- ಪೂರ್ವಭಾವಿ ಬಹಿರಂಗಪಡಿಸುವಿಕೆ: ಇದು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳು ಕೆಲವು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪೂರ್ವಭಾವಿಯಾಗಿ ಬಹಿರಂಗಪಡಿಸಲು ಕಡ್ಡಾಯಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಅಂದರೇ, ವಾರ್ಷಿಕ ವರದಿಗಳು ಮುಂತಾದ ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ವಯಂ ಪ್ರೇರಿತವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಕಟಿಸಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಯ ರಕ್ಷಣೆ: RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಆದ್ಯತೆ ನೀಡುವುದರಿಂದ, ಆಂತರಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಾಗುವ ವಂಚನೆ-ಮೋಸಗಳು ಹಾಗೂ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳ ಸ್ವಹಿತಾಸಕ್ತಿಗೆ ಮಾರಕವಾದ ಅಸ್ತವಾಗಿ ಬಳಕೆಯಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ.
- ನಾಗರಿಕರ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ಒತ್ತು: ಇದು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ನೇರವಾಗಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡುವುದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಜನರನ್ನು ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಕ್ರಿಯರನ್ನಾಗಿಸುವುದರೊಂದಿಗೆ ಅವರನ್ನು ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾಲ್ಗೊಳ್ಳುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದೆ.

ಆರ್ಟಿಐ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಬಲ ಸಾಧನವಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರರನ್ನಾಗಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಅದರ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಚರಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಒತ್ತಾಯಿಸಲು ಅನುವು ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದಾಗ್ಯೂ, ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕಿನ ಜಾರಿಯಲ್ಲಿನ ಅಸಮಾನತೆಗಳು ಅದರ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಅಡ್ಡಿಯಾಗುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ಅವಲೋಕಿಸ ಬೇಕಾದ ಅಂಶವಾಗಿದೆ.

RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಗುರಿ ಮತ್ತು ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳು

- RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಿಂದ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಕೋರಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತ ಮತ್ತು ಇತರ ವಲಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರವನ್ನು ನಿಯಂತ್ರಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ನಿರ್ಣಾಯಕ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.
- RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ನೌಕರಶಾಹಿ ವರ್ಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಚರಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಒತ್ತು ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತ ವರ್ಗ ಹಾಗೂ ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಶ್ನಿಸಲು ನಾಗರಿಕರಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾಗೃತಿ ಮೂಡಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಇದು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರವೇಶಿಸುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಗಣನೀಯವಾಗಿ ಸುಧಾರಿಸಿದೆ.
- ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳನ್ನು ತಮ್ಮ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರವನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸಿದೆ.

ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣಗಳು

ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ ಎರಡು ಕಾರಣಗಳನ್ನು ನೋಡಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ, ಅವುಗಳೆಂದರೇ,

ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯ ಕೊರತೆ

ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಆಡಳಿತ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯ ಕೊರತೆಯು ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಲು ಮೂಲ ಕಾರಣಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದಲ್ಲದೆ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯ ಕೊರತೆಯಿಂದ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಂಗದಲ್ಲಿ ನೇರ ಮತ್ತು ನಿಷ್ಠೂರವಾದ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವಲ್ಲಿ ಅಸಹಜ ಮನೋಸ್ಥಿತಿಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಪ್ರತಿ ಹಂತದಲ್ಲಿ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಸಂಗತಿಯಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ.

ದುರ್ಬಲ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಲ್ಲದ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳು

ಕಾನೂನುಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ನಿಬಂಧನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಾಗಿರುವ ಭಾರತದ ಹಲವು ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು ದುರ್ಬಲವಾಗಿವೆ ಅಥವಾ ರಾಜಿ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತವೆ. ಇದರಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾನೂನು ಜಾರಿ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು, ನ್ಯಾಯಾಂಗ ಮತ್ತು ಮೇಲ್ವಿಚಾರಣಾ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು ಸೇರಿವೆ. ದುರ್ಬಲ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು ಭ್ರಷ್ಟ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡಲು ವಿಫಲವಾಗಬಹುದು ಮತ್ತು ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರವನ್ನು ಸುಗಮಗೊಳಿಸಬಹುದು.

ಅಂತರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತದ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರದ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಗತಿಗಳು

ಕಳೆದ ಕೆಲವು ದಶಕಗಳಿಂದ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರದ ಪ್ರಮಾಣವು ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಅಂತರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಸರಕಾರೇತರ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆ ಟ್ರಾನ್ಸ್‌ಪರೆನ್ಸಿ ಇಂಟರ್‌ನ್ಯಾಷನಲ್ ಬಿಡುಗಡೆಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಸೂಚ್ಯಂಕದಿಂದ ತಿಳಿದುಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

2013 ರಿಂದ 2023ರ ವರೆಗಿನ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರ ಸೂಚ್ಯಂಕ

ಕ್ರ.ಸಂ	ವರ್ಷ	ಭಾರತದ ಸ್ಥಾನ/ರ్యాಂಕ್
1	2013	94
2	2014	85
3	2015	76
4	2016	79
5	2017	81
6	2018	78
7	2019	80
8	2020	86
9	2021	85
10	2022	85
11	2023	93

ಮೂಲ: Transparency International NGO Report.

ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ನಿಬಂಧನೆಗಳು

RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಹಲವಾರು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ನಿಬಂಧನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಅವುಗಳೆಂದರೆ,

- ಸೆಕ್ಷನ್ 2(ಹೆಚ್): ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರದಿಂದ ಧನಸಹಾಯ ಪಡೆದ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು ಸೇರಿದಂತೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಪ್ರಾಧಿಕಾರಗಳನ್ನು ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಸೆಕ್ಷನ್ 4(1) (ಬಿ): ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಏಜೆನ್ಸಿಗಳಿಂದ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪೂರ್ವಭಾವಿಯಾಗಿ ಬಹಿರಂಗಪಡಿಸುವುದನ್ನು ಕಡ್ಡಾಯಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಸೆಕ್ಷನ್ 6: ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಕೋರಲು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಸರಳವಾದ ಕಾರ್ಯವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ವಿವರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಸೆಕ್ಷನ್ 7: ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಕೋರಿಕೆಯ ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳ ಅವಧಿಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಸೆಕ್ಷನ್ 20: ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಸಮಯಕ್ಕೆ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ನೀಡಲು ವಿಫಲವಾದರೆ ದಂಡವನ್ನು ವಿಧಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಈ ಕಾನೂನು ನಾಗರಿಕರು ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ನಡುವಿನ ಸಂಬಂಧವನ್ನು ವೃದ್ಧಿಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಜನರು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ತೊಡಗಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಅನುವುಮಾಡಿಕೊಟ್ಟಿದೆ. ಅಷ್ಟೇ ಅಲ್ಲದೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರಿಗೆ ಉತ್ತರದಾಯಿಯಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಇದು ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಸಾಧನವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಆಡಳಿತದ ಮೇಲೆ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಪರಿಣಾಮ

ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು (ಆರ್‌ಟಿಐ) ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಭಾರತದ ಆಡಳಿತದ ಮೇಲೆ ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ ಪರಿಣಾಮ ಬೀರಿದೆ. ಇದು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಿಂದ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ನೀಡುವುದರ ಮೂಲಕ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಟ್ಟಿದೆ. ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ನಾಗರಿಕರು ತಮ್ಮ ಸರ್ಕಾರದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸಂವಹನ ನಡೆಸುವ ವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ಮಾರ್ಪಡಿಸಿದೆ. ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನ ಅಂಶಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಆಡಳಿತದ ಮೇಲೆ ಬೀರುವ ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಯಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಅವುಗಳೆಂದರೆ.

ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುವುದು

RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಹಲವಾರು ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಅವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ,

- ಉತ್ತರದಾಯಿತ್ವ: ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ನೀತಿ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳಿಗೆ ಉತ್ತರದಾಯಿತ್ವ ಆಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಇವರುಗಳು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಯೋಜನೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರರು ಆಗಿರಬೇಕಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಿಂದ ನೋಡುವುದಾದರೆ ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಕಾರ್ಯಾಂಗ ಅಥವಾ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಶಾಹಿ ವರ್ಗವನ್ನು ಎಚ್ಚರಿಕೆಯಿಂದ ತಮ್ಮ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುವಂತೆ ನೋಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಲ್ಲಿ ತಕ್ಕ ಮಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಯಶಸ್ವಿಯಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ.

- ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸುವುದು: ಅನ್ಯ ಕಾರಣಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡದೆ ಸೂಚಿತ ಸಮಯದೊಳಗೆ (30 ದಿನದೊಳಗೆ) ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳು ಅನ್ಯ ಕಾರಣಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡದೆ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಬೇಕು. ತಪ್ಪಿದ್ದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಬಂಧಿತ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಪ್ರಕರಣಗಳನ್ನು ದಾಖಲಿಸುವ ಮತ್ತು ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷೆ ವಿಧಿಸುವ ಅವಕಾಶವಿದೆ.

ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರವನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡುವುದು

ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ, RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರವನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಹೇಗೆಂದರೆ,

- ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯಂತೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರು ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಪಡೆದು ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ವಿವಿಧ ಇಲಾಖೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಭಾಗಗಳಲ್ಲಿನ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಅಸಮರ್ಥ ಆಡಳಿತದ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ವಲಯಕ್ಕೆ ತಿಳಿಸುವುದರಿಂದ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಕಾರಾತ್ಮಕ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಲಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ.
- ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲನೆಗೆ ಮುಕ್ತವಾಗಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ನೈತಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತವನ್ನು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುವುದು.
- ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರು ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳ ಕಾರ್ಯವೈಖರಿಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರಶ್ನಿಸಬಹುದಾದ ಅವಕಾಶ ಇರುವುದರಿಂದ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಗತಿ ಸಾಧಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಸಹಭಾಗಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಸುಧಾರಿಸುವುದು

ಆರ್‌ಟಿಐ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಒಳಗೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಿದೆ:

- ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಫಲವಾಗಿ ನಾಗರಿಕರು ಇಂದು ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ನೀತಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳ ಬಗೆಗಿನ ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ತೊಡಗುವಂತಾಗಿರುವುದು ಉತ್ತಮ ಆಡಳಿತದ ಸೂಚಕವಾಗಿದೆ.
- ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಳು, ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯುಳ್ಳ ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ಕಲ್ಪಿಸುತ್ತಿದೆ.
- ಇದು ಸ್ಥಳೀಯ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮುದಾಯದ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುತ್ತಿದೆ.

ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಪಾತ್ರ

ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು (ಆರ್‌ಟಿಐ) ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರದಿಂದ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುವ ಪ್ರಬಲ ಸಾಧನವಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಚರಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಕ್ತತೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯನ್ನು ತರಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರು ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಪ್ರಕಾರ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ಕೆಲವು ನಿಯಮಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಪಾಲಿಸ ಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಅವುಗಳು,

- **ಮಾಹಿತಿ ವಿನಂತಿಗಳು:** ನಾಗರಿಕರು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳಿಂದ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಕೋರಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

- **ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಕಾಲಮಿತಿ:** ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರು ಕೋರಿರುವ ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಕಾಲಮಿತಿಯೊಳಗೆ ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ರಿಯಿಸಬೇಕು.
- **ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಜಾಗೃತಿ:** RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಅಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಅವರ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ತಿಳಿಸಲು ಅಭಿಯಾನಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸಲಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ.

ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನದಲ್ಲಿನ ಸವಾಲುಗಳು

ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳ್ಳುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಮಹತ್ತರವಾದ ಯಶಸ್ಸನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸಿದ ಹೊರತಾಗಿಯೂ, RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಕೆಲವು ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾದವುಗಳೆಂದರೆ,

- **ಅರಿವಿನ ಕೊರತೆ:** ದೇಶದ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಜನರಿಗೆ RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಇರುವ ನೀತಿ-ನಿಯಮಗಳ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ಅರಿವು ಇಲ್ಲದಿರುವುದು ಒಂದು ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಅನೇಕ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಬೇಕು ಅಥವಾ ಅವರು ಯಾವ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಕೋರಬಹುದು ಎಂಬುದು ತಿಳಿದಿಲ್ಲ. ಈ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ನೌಕರಶಾಹಿ ವರ್ಗಕ್ಕೆ ವರದಾನವಾಗಿದೆ.
- **ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳಿಂದ ಪ್ರತಿರೋಧ:** ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಜಾರಿಗೆ ಬಂದು ಇಂದಿಗೆ ಎರಡು ದಶಕಗಳಾದರೂ, ಇಂದಿಗೂ ಕೆಲವು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳು ಮಾಹಿತಿ ನೀಡುವುದನ್ನು ವಿರೋಧಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಇದನ್ನು ಸರಿಯಾದ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸುಧಾರಿಸಲು ಸಫಲರಾಗದಿರುವುದು ಶೋಚನೀಯವಾಗಿದೆ.
- **ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿನ ವಿಳಂಬಗಳು:** ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಬಹಿರಂಗಪಡಿಸುವಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಆಗಾಗ್ಗೆ ವಿಳಂಬಗಳು ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತವೆ, ಇದು ನಾಗರಿಕರನ್ನು ನಿರಾಶೆಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತಿದೆ.
- ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಕುರಿತು ನಾಗರಿಕರಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರಾಸಕ್ತಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚುತ್ತಿರುವುದು.

ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ತುಲನಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆ:

ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು (ಆರ್‌ಟಿಐ) ಕಾಯ್ದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಇತರ ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿನ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ (Freedom of Information-FOI) ಕಾಯ್ದೆಗಳು ಒಂದೇ ರೀತಿಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶಗಳನ್ನು ಪೂರೈಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಆದರೆ ಅವುಗಳ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನ ಮತ್ತು ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಿನ್ನವಾಗಿವೆ. RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳಿಂದ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದರೆ FOI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರವೇಶವನ್ನು ಮಿತಿಗೊಳಿಸಬಹುದಾದ ವಿಶಾಲವಾದ ವಿನಾಯಿತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲವು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸಗಳಿವೆ,

- ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿ: RTI ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ, ಆದರೆ FOI ಕೆಲವು ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊರತುಪಡಿಸಬಹುದು.
- ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ರಿಯೆ ಸಮಯ: RTI 30 ದಿನಗಳೊಳಗೆ ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ರಿಯೆಯನ್ನು ಕಡ್ಡಾಯಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ, ಆದರೆ FOI ದೀರ್ಘಾವಧಿಯ ಸಮಯಾವಧಿಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಬಹುದು.

- ಅನುಸರಣೆಗೆ ದಂಡಗಳು: ಮಾಹಿತಿ ನೀಡಲು ವಿಫಲರಾದ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳಿಗೆ RTI ಕಟ್ಟುನಿಟ್ಟಾದ ದಂಡಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ, ಆದರೆ FOI ಅಂತಹ ದಂಡಗಳನ್ನು ಜಾರಿಗೊಳಿಸದಿರಬಹುದು.

ಅಂತರರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಸ್ತರವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳು

ವಿವಿಧ ದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಆಡಳಿತ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸಿರುವ ಅಂತರರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳು RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಸ್ಪೂರ್ತಿ ನೀಡಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ,

- **ಸ್ವೀಡನ್:** ತನ್ನ ಪ್ರಬಲವಾದ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೆಸರುವಾಸಿಯಾಗಿರುವ ಸ್ವೀಡನ್ ದೇಶವು ತನ್ನ ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ದಾಖಲೆಗಳನ್ನು ಮುಕ್ತವಾಗಿ ತಿಳಿಯಲು ಮತ್ತು ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ರಿಯಿಸಲು ಅನುಮತಿಸಿದೆ. ಇದು ದೇಶದ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಕ್ತತೆಯ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಇಂದು ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಚಾರವನ್ನು ನಿಯಂತ್ರಿಸುವ ಕಾರ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ದೇಶವು ಉತ್ತಮ ಸಾಧನೆ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಇದರ ಪ್ರತಿಫಲವೆಂಬಂತೆ ಪ್ರತಿ ವರ್ಷದ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಚಾರ ಸೂಚ್ಯಂಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ತಮ ಸ್ಥಾನವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿನ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕ ಒಂಬಡ್ಡಮನ್ ಕಾನೂನುನ್ನು ಭಾರತ ಎರವಲು ಪಡೆದಿದೆ.
- **ಕೆನಡಾ:** ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ಪ್ರವೇಶ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಖಾತ್ರಿಪಡಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಇದು ವಿಳಂಬಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ವಿನಾಯಿತಿಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತಿದೆ.
- **ಯುನೈಟೆಡ್ ಸ್ಟೇಟ್ಸ್:** ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಬಹಿರಂಗಪಡಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಇದು ಮಿತಿಮೀರಿದ ಪುನರಾವರ್ತನೆಗಳಿಗಾಗಿ ಟೀಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಎದುರಿಸುತ್ತಿದೆ.

ಈ ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗಳು ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿ ಜಾರಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಜಾಗೃತಿಯ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಎತ್ತಿ ತೋರಿಸುತ್ತವೆ.

ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯನ್ನು ಬೆಂಬಲಿಸುವ ಕಾನೂನು ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಂಸ್ಥಿಕ ಚೌಕಟ್ಟು

ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಆಯೋಗಗಳ ಪಾತ್ರ

ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆ (RTI) ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಆಯೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಿದೆ. ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನದ ಮೇಲ್ವಿಚಾರಣೆಗೆ ಈ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯಾಗಿವೆ. ನಾಗರಿಕರು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ಸರ್ವರೀತಿಯಿಂದಲೂ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರರಾಗಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳು ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಲು ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿತವಾಗಿರುವ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸಬೇಕಾಗಿರುವುದು ಕಡ್ಡಾಯವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ರಾಜ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಳಹಂತದ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ವಿಭಾಗದ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳು ರಾಜ್ಯ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಆಯೋಗದ ಆಯುಕ್ತರುಗಳಿಗೆ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಕೋರಿರುವ ಮನವಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಮೇಲ್ಮನವಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ದೂರುಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡುವ ಅಧಿಕಾರವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ.

ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಜಾರಿಗಾಗಿ ಸಾಂಸ್ಥಿಕ ಕಾರ್ಯವಿಧಾನಗಳು

RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯನ್ನು ಬೆಂಬಲಿಸಲು, ವಿವಿಧ ಸಾಂಸ್ಥಿಕ ಕಾರ್ಯವಿಧಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಅವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ

- **ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳು (PIO):** ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುವ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯನ್ನು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಇಲಾಖೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಗೊತ್ತುಪಡಿಸಿದ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಅವರುಗಳನ್ನು **PIO** ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಇವರುಗಳು ಕೋರಿರುವ ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕ ಹಂತದಲ್ಲಿ ನೀಡುವ ಕಾರ್ಯಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ.
- **ತರಬೇತಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳು:** ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ PIOಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಅವರ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸೂಕ್ತ ತರಬೇತಿ ನೀಡುವ ಅವಕಾಶ ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.
- **ಜಾಗೃತಿ ಅಭಿಯಾನಗಳು:** RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಅವರ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ತಿಳಿಸಲು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಸೂಕ್ತ ಸಲಹೆ ಸೂಚನೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡುವ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನ ನಡೆಯುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ವತಿಯಿಂದ ವಿವಿಧ ಹಂತಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾಗೃತಿ ಅಭಿಯಾನವನ್ನು ಹಮ್ಮಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದು ಒಂದು ಹಂತದಲ್ಲಿ ಜನರನ್ನು ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಪಡೆಯಲು ಅರ್ಹರನ್ನಾಗಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಮತ್ತೊಂದು ಹಂತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡಲು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಆರ್‌ಟಿಐ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯನ್ನು ಬೆಂಬಲಿಸುವ ಕಾನೂನು ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಂಸ್ಥಿಕ ಚೌಕಟ್ಟು ಅದರ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಅತ್ಯಗತ್ಯ. ನಾಗರಿಕರು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಮೂಲಕ, ಈ ಕಾರ್ಯವಿಧಾನಗಳು ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆಯ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಅರಿವು ನೀಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯಂತಹ ಕಾನೂನುಗಳಿಂದ ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಮೇಲ್ವಿಚಾರಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಕಾಪಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ.

ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಭವಿಷ್ಯದ ರೂಪರೇಷೆಗಳು

ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಲು ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆ (ಆರ್‌ಟಿಐ)ಯನ್ನು ಇನ್ನಷ್ಟು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಗೊಳಿಸಬೇಕಿದೆ. ಅದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನ ಕೆಲವು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಬೇಕಿದೆ.

ಸಂಭಾವ್ಯ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ತಿದ್ದುಪಡಿಗಳು

- ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಕೋರಿಕೆಯ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯನ್ನು ಸರಳೀಕರಣಗೊಳಿಸುವುದು.
- ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಪ್ರದೇಶಗಳಲ್ಲಿ RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಅರಿವು ಮೂಡಿಸುವುದು.
- ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ತಮ್ಮ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಗಳನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳಿಗೆ ತರಬೇತಿಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುವುದು.

ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯನ್ನು ಬಲಪಡಿಸುವ ತಂತ್ರಗಳು

RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಲು, ಹಲವಾರು ಕಾರ್ಯತಂತ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಬಹುದು. ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ

- ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಕೋರಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ತ್ವರಿತವಾಗಿ ಪರಿಹರಿಸುವ ಇಲಾಖೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಬಹುಮಾನ ನೀಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವುದು.
- ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳು ಅನುಸರಿಸಲು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟ ಮಾರ್ಗಸೂಚಿಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸುವುದು. ಈ ಮೂಲಕ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ನೀಡುವಲ್ಲಿ ಉಂಟಾಗುವ ಗೊಂದಲ ಮತ್ತು ಅನಿಶ್ಚಿತತೆಯನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡುವುದು.
- ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಪಡೆಯುವಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಳಂಬ ಅಥವಾ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ವರದಿ ಮಾಡಲು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ರಿಯೆ ಕಾರ್ಯವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ರಚಿಸುವುದು. ಇದರಿಂದ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರಿಗೆ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಪಡೆಯುವಲ್ಲಿ ಆಗುವ ವಿಳಂಬ ಮತ್ತು ದೋಷಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟತೆ ಮೂಡುವುದು.

ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನದ ಪಾತ್ರ:

ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯನ್ನು ಸುಧಾರಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನವು ಮಹತ್ವದ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗೆ,

- ಆರ್‌ಟಿಐ ಕೋರಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸುಲಭವಾಗಿ ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಲು ಆನ್‌ಲೈನ್ ಪೋರ್ಟಲ್‌ಗಳನ್ನು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಪಡಿಸಬಹುದು.
- ಮೊಬೈಲ್ ಅಪ್ಲಿಕೇಶನ್‌ಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ನಾಗರಿಕರು ತಮ್ಮ ವಿನಂತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಟ್ಯಾಕ್ ಮಾಡಲು ಮತ್ತು ನವೀಕರಣಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ವೀಕರಿಸಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡಬಹುದು.
- ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಕೋರಿಕೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿನ ಪ್ರವೃತ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸಲು ಡೇಟಾ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆಯನ್ನು ಬಳಸಬಹುದು. ಇದು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಕಾಳಜಿಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.

ವಿವಿಧ ವಲಯಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಪರಿಣಾಮ:

ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು (ಆರ್‌ಟಿಐ) ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಭಾರತದ ವಿವಿಧ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಗಮನಾರ್ಹವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರಿದೆ. ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಆಡಳಿತ ವಲಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸಿದೆ. ಅದಲ್ಲದೆ ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಾಗಿ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಯಿಡಲು ಅಧಿಕಾರ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದರಿಂದ ಆಡಳಿತವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಮುಕ್ತಗೊಳಿಸುವಂತಾಗಿದೆ.

ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ವಲಯದ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳು:

RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ವಲಯದ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಚರಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ. ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ

- ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ವೆಚ್ಚದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವುದು.
- ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಶ್ನಿಸಲು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡುವುದು.

- ಅಧಿಕಾರಶಾಹಿಗಳ ವಿಳಂಬ ನೀತಿಯನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡುವುದು.

ನಾಗರಿಕ ಸಮಾಜ ಮತ್ತು NGOಗಳು:

ನಾಗರಿಕ ಸಮಾಜ ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರೇತರ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯನ್ನು ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನಂತೆ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡಿವೆ

- ಅಂಚಿನಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳಿಗೆ ರಕ್ಷಣೆಗಾಗಿ.
- ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ನೀತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಮೇಲ್ವಿಚಾರಣೆ ಮಾಡಲು.
- ನಾಗರಿಕರ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಜಾಗೃತಿ ಮೂಡಿಸಲು.

ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯ ಮೂಲಕ ನಾಗರಿಕರ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣ:

ಅಂಚಿನಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳ ಸಬಲೀಕರಣ:

ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆ (ಆರ್‌ಟಿಐ) ನಾಗರಿಕರನ್ನು ಸಬಲೀಕರಣಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಬಲ ಸಾಧನವಾಗಿದೆ. ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಅಂಚಿನಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಸಮುದಾಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳಿಂದ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ವಿನಂತಿಸಲು ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ, RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಅನ್ಯಾಯಗಳ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಹೋರಾಡಲು ಮತ್ತು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಕೇಳಲು ಅನುವು ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಇಂತಹ ಕ್ರಮಗಳು ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕನ್ನು ಬಲಪಡಿಸಿದೆ. ಭ್ರಷ್ಟಾಚಾರವನ್ನು ಬಹಿರಂಗಪಡಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಭ್ರಷ್ಟ ರಾಜಕಾರಣಿಗಳನ್ನು-ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳನ್ನು ಅವರ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟ ಕೃತ್ಯಗಳಿಂದ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಜನರನ್ನು ರಕ್ಷಿಸುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ನೀಡುವುದು.

ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯ ಚಳವಳಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾತ್ರ:

ಆರ್‌ಟಿಐ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ವಿವಿಧ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನ್ಯಾಯ ಚಳವಳಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹತ್ವದ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಯೋಜನೆಗಳು/ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿನ ಅಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಬಯಲಿಗೆಳೆಯಲು ಕಾರ್ಯಕರ್ತರು ಈ ಕಾನೂನನ್ನು ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇದರಿಂದ ಉದ್ದೇಶಿತ ಸ್ವೀಕೃತದಾರರಿಗೆ, ಫಲಾನುಭವಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಗಳನ್ನು ತಲುಪುವಂತೆ ಖಾತ್ರಿಪಡಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗೆ, RTI ವಿನಂತಿಗಳು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿವೇತನಗಳ ವಿತರಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿನ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸಗಳನ್ನು ಬಹಿರಂಗಪಡಿಸಿವೆ. ಇದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ತನಿಖೆಗಳು ನಡೆದಿವೆ/ನಡೆಯುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಪರಿಣಾಮವಾಗಿ ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸುಧಾರಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ತರುವಂತೆ ಪ್ರೇರೇಪಿಸುತ್ತಿವೆ.

ಮಾಹಿತಿಯುಕ್ತ ನಾಗರಿಕರನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸುವುದು:

ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವುದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಸಕ್ರಿಯವಾಗಿ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ನಾಗರಿಕರನ್ನು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯುಳ್ಳ ನಾಗರಿಕರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ. ಇದರಿಂದ ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕರು ಸಂಭಾಷಣೆ ಮತ್ತು ನಿರ್ಧಾರ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ತೊಡಗಬಹುದು. ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯುಳ್ಳ ನಾಗರಿಕರ ಕೆಲವು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಗಳು ಇಲ್ಲಿವೆ:

- **ಹೆಚ್ಚಿದ ಹೊಣೆಗಾರಿಕೆ:** ನಾಗರಿಕರು ತಮ್ಮ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡಬಹುದು.
- **ಸಕ್ರಿಯ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ:** ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯುಳ್ಳ ನಾಗರಿಕರು ಆಡಳಿತದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವ ಸಾಧ್ಯತೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು.

RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ನಾಗರಿಕರು ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ನಡುವಿನ ಸಂಬಂಧವನ್ನು ಬಲಪಡಿಸುವುದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಇದು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯುತವನ್ನಾಗಿಸಿದೆ. ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯುವ ಹಕ್ಕನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ನೀಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ, RTI ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ಮೂಲಾಧಾರವಾಗಿದೆ. ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬ ನಾಗರಿಕನು ಆಡಳಿತವನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕತೆಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸಬಹುದೆಂದು ಈ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದಲ್ಲದೆ ಭ್ರಷ್ಟ ಮತ್ತು ಆಡಳಿತದ ದುರುಪಯೋಗದ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಹೋರಾಡಲು ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಪ್ರಬಲವಾದ ಸಾಧನವಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಸರ್ಕಾರದಿಂದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ನಾಗರಿಕರಿಗೆ ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಕಾನೂನು ಜನರಿಗೆ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕೇಳಲು ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತರಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ಅಧಿಕಾರ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಅಂಶವು ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.

ಸಮಾರೋಪ

ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಹಕ್ಕು ಕಾಯ್ದೆ (ಆರ್‌ಟಿಐ) ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ಹೇಗೆ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬುದರಲ್ಲಿ ದೊಡ್ಡ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿದೆ. ಸರ್ಕಾರವು ಏನು ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಅರಿಯಲು ಜನರಿಗೆ ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕೇಳಲು ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತರಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ಅವರಿಗೆ ಸುಲಭವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬರೂ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ಮತ್ತು ತಿಳಿದುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಈ ಕಾನೂನನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದು ನ್ಯಾಯಯುತ ಮತ್ತು ಮುಕ್ತ ಸರ್ಕಾರ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿದೆ. ಆದಾಗ್ಯೂ, ಇನ್ನೂ ಕೆಲವು ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಸರಿಪಡಿಸಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ. ಇನ್ನೂ ಅನೇಕ ಜನರಿಗೆ RTI ಅನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ಬಳಸುವುದು ಎಂದು ತಿಳಿದಿಲ್ಲ, ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಕೆಲವು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಕಚೇರಿಗಳು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಹಂಚಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಿದ್ಧರಿರುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. RTI ಅನ್ನು ನಿಜವಾಗಿಯೂ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಮಾಡಲು, ನಾವು ಅದರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ನೀಡಬೇಕು ಮತ್ತು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸಲು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು ಸಿದ್ಧವಾಗಿವೆ ಎಂದು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ. ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆಯಾಗಿ, ಆರ್‌ಟಿಐ ಕಾಯ್ದೆಯು ಸರ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯುತ ಮತ್ತು ಪಾರದರ್ಶಕವಾಗಿಸಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುವ ಪ್ರಬಲ ಸಾಧನವಾಗಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಅದರ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವನ್ನು ತಲುಪಲು ಬೆಂಬಲ ಮತ್ತು ಸುಧಾರಣೆಯ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿದೆ.

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